

Artificial stepwise increases in homogenized surface air temperature data invalidate published climate warming claims for Canada

Joseph Hickey, * PhD

Correlation Research in the Public Interest (correlation-canada.org)

* joseph.hickey@alumni.ucalgary.ca

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Hickey, J. Artificial stepwise increases in homogenized surface air temperature data invalidate published climate warming claims for Canada, CORRELATION Research in the Public Interest, Report, 23 December 2025, <https://correlation-canada.org/artificial-stepwise-increases-in-temperature-data-canada/>

Abstract

Continental-scale multi-decadal temperature climate trend evaluations rely on networks of land-based weather stations. Long-term surface air temperature records from the said stations are affected by many biasing factors, related to changes to instrumentation, observation

methods and procedures, and the environment surrounding the instruments. In determining long-term temperature trends, temperature records are adjusted and homogenized in an attempt to correct for gradual biases and sudden discontinuities. The Canadian government (Environment Canada) provides the Adjusted and Homogenized Canadian Climate Data (AHCCD) to the public and research community for use in long-term temperature trend analysis in Canada, which is promoted and accepted as reliable data. In this report, I show that a significant non-climatic artifact exists in the AHCCD, which is a stepwise increase of approximately 1°C in magnitude occurring at 1998 in the annual average temperature records for most AHCCD stations across Canada, and that this 1°C increase occurring at 1998 can, on its own, be responsible for essentially all of the claimed warming (of approximately 1-2°C) calculated for Canada over the past six or seven decades. This is based on the temperature data itself, and the institutional context is revealed through access to information (ATI) documents. The reported climate warming of Canada appears to be entirely from a temperature measurement artifact.

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Abbreviations used in this report

AHCCD	Adjusted and Homogenized Canadian Climate Data
ATI	Access to Information

1 Introduction

An unavoidable problem in long-term temperature trend analysis is the fact that temperature records spanning multiple decades are affected by many factors that can artificially bias or skew

the measured temperatures, causing either sudden discontinuities (shifts upwards or downwards) or gradual increases or decreases in the data that are non-climatic in origin (Peterson et al. 1998; Vincent and Gullett 1999; Runnalls and Oke 2006; Pielke Sr., Davey, et al. 2007; Pielke Sr., Nielsen-Gammon, et al. 2007; Trewin 2010; Whitfield 2014; Vincent et al. 2009; 2012; 2020; Wan et al. 2025).

As Peterson et al. (1998) noted, “most decade- to century-scale time series of atmospheric data have been adversely impacted by inhomogeneities caused by, for example, changes in instrumentation, station moves, changes in the local environment such as urbanization, or the introduction of different observing practices like a new formula for calculating mean daily temperature or different observation times.”

Consequently, and given the intense political interest in so-called climate change, a major part of the work of national meteorological institutes has been the construction of “homogenized” temperature records, which attempt to adjust and correct for biasing factors in order to produce long-term (multi-decade or longer) time-series of daily, monthly, or annual temperatures for particular geographic locations. The homogenized datasets are then used in analyses of temperature trends and for constructing gridded temperature datasets used in global temperature trend and extreme value analysis, and computational climate modeling (Peterson et al. 1998; Vincent and Gullett 1999; Vincent et al. 2012; 2020; Osborn et al. 2021; Wan et al. 2025; Zhang et al. 2021; Donat et al. 2013; Dunn et al. 2020).

Often, a long-term temperature record for a particular location is created by joining together temperature records from different, nearby stations (or station sites, in the case of a single station that has moved) with data spanning different but contiguous or overlapping time periods. The different station sites necessarily have different surroundings, may be located at different altitudes, and might use different types of instruments, instrument housing apparatuses, or observation procedures. This can produce a stepwise shift in the constructed long-term temperature record, or gradual biases affecting the long-term record. For this reason, such constructed long-term records are typically analyzed with the goal of detecting stepwise shifts or gradual biases, and the data points for one or more of the joined segments of the long-term record may be adjusted in some way, in order to create a “homogenized” long-term record for use in long-term trend analysis (Vincent et al. 2020).

In other cases involving data from a single weather station (with no joining together of records), a stepwise shift or gradual increase or decrease in a temperature record may be adjusted up or down if it is attributed to a documented instrumental or environmental change at the station, or otherwise detected using manual or automatic methods (Vincent et al. 2020).

However, many biasing factors, which can be as simple as the growth of trees over many years in the vicinity of the thermometer, aging of the thermometer (off-calibration drift), or the flaking off of paint on the screen that shields the thermometer from solar radiation (see section

3.2.2 of this report and the references therein), can go undetected, such that their effect, whether stepwise or gradual, influences the long-term trends calculated from the temperature series in a manner that is not reflective of regional climate variability but rather only the conditions in the local surroundings of the thermometer.

In other words, the homogenized surface air temperature records constituting the fundamental basis of many long-term temperature trend analyses must be understood as having been subjected to a significant degree of intentional manual and algorithmic modification (Heller 2010; 2012; 2015; 2018; 2023), while also being affected by many potential undetected or undocumented biases that can skew the record but for which no adjustments have been made.

In Canada, homogenized temperature time-series data have been provided by Environment Canada (now officially known as Environment and Climate Change Canada) since the 1990s, and updated and expanded several times since then (Gullett et al. 1992; Vincent and Gullett 1999; Vincent et al. 2012; 2020; Wan et al. 2025). These data, called the Adjusted and Homogenized Canadian Climate Data (AHCCD), consist of long-term, homogenized time-series of daily minimum, maximum, and mean (average of daily minimum and daily maximum) surface air temperatures for hundreds of stations across Canada. The AHCCD has been used as-provided by Environment Canada in many global-scale temperature trend studies without any additional modifications or adjustments (Donat et al. 2013; Dunn et al. 2020; Osborn et al. 2021; Zhang et al. 2021).

In this report, the term “AHCCD station” refers to the station site that Environment Canada associates with a particular long-term homogenized temperature record (even if the record was constructed by joining data segments from different nearby or relocated stations). For example, Environment Canada constructed the AHCCD record for Moncton, New Brunswick by joining together temperature records from three different sites spanning 1898-1940 (station id 8103100), 1940-2012 (station id 8103200), and 2012-2022 (station id 8103201). Environment Canada associates the station id number of the most recent of the three sites (8103201), and the latitude-longitude coordinate for the site with station id 8103201, to the AHCCD record for Moncton.

Using the AHCCD, many authors have assessed that surface air temperatures across Canada have increased by 1-2°C over the past six or seven decades. For example, Vincent et al. (2020) report a 1.74°C increase in annual mean temperature for Canada over the period 1948-2018 and a 1.62°C increase in annual mean temperature for southern Canada for 1900-2018, using the 3rd generation of the AHCCD. Bank of Canada authors Amano et al. (2021) reported temperature increases ranging from 1.16°C to 2.98°C for specific AHCCD stations over the time period 1960-2019, and a mean group estimator result of 1.47°C of warming for southern Canadian AHCCD stations for 1960-2019, using the 3rd generation of the AHCCD. Wan et al.

(2025) report a 2.08°C increase in the annual mean temperature for Canada for the period 1948-2023, using the 4th generation of the AHCCD.

In this report, I show that the temperature records for many AHCCD stations across Canada exhibit a stepwise increase of approximately 1°C in magnitude occurring at 1998 in the time-series of annual averages of daily mean, maximum, and minimum temperatures. The said stepwise increase at 1998 occurs between data segments with essentially zero slope for multiple decades before and after 1998, for many AHCCD stations across the country. I refer to this apparent artifact as the “1998 step-increase feature”. 1998 is the year in which a set of 72 Canadian reference climatological stations were first added to the Global Climate Observing System (Milewska and Vincent 2016).

I sent figures showing the 1998 step-increase feature in the temperature records of many AHCCD stations to the Environment Canada researchers responsible for creating the AHCCD in emails in June and July of 2021, when I was employed as a data scientist at the Bank of Canada. These emails have since been obtained via an Access to Information (ATI) request to Environment Canada. The main emails of interest from the ATI release are copied in the Results section of this report (section 3), and the entire ATI release can be read in Appendix F.

The first part of the Results section of this report, section 3.1, shows and explains the 1998 step-increase feature, its presence across most of Canada, and its uniqueness as the only large and widespread discontinuity in the AHCCD dataset.

Section 3.2 shows and explains my emails to Environment Canada researchers alerting them to the 1998 step-increase feature and arguing that it must be of artificial, non-climatic origin, and could, on its own, account for most of the calculated warming for Canadian AHCCD stations over the past several decades.

Section 3.2 also shows the email responses of senior Environment Canada Research Climatologist Lucie A. Vincent. In her responses, Vincent did not provide an explanation for the 1998 step-increase feature, but rather stated she had “quickly checked the metadata for some of the stations” and, on that basis, affirmed that the step-increase feature would not have been caused by the introduction of automated weather stations during the 1990s. In her final response, Vincent stated that “[w]e have not detected a positive shift around 1998 in the annual mean temperature of the selected stations due to automation or any other non-climatic causes” and that “[t]his shift [the 1998 step-increase feature] identified visually when the time series is focused on the 1960-2020 period is probably due to climate variability only.”

Additional emails released in the ATI request revealed that there were more than 10,000 instances of days for which the daily minimum temperature was greater than the daily maximum temperature, in the 2nd generation of the AHCCD. This issue is explained in section 3.3

of this report, along with Environment Canada's responses after being alerted to the issue by Bank of Canada Economist Julien McDonald-Guimond.

Section 4 contains a discussion, including a demonstration, in section 4.2, that Environment Canada's failure to "detect" the large (approximately 1°C in magnitude) stepwise shifts in many AHCCD records appears to be attributable to the fact that Environment Canada's applied step-detection method fails to capture steps that are present in the records for pairs of neighbouring AHCCD stations. The said demonstration uses Environment Canada researchers' own figures from their paper presenting the 3rd generation of the AHCCD (Vincent et al. 2020), for two AHCCD stations exhibiting some of the most striking examples of the 1998 step-increase feature (Moncton and Fredericton).

Section 4.3 shows that the 1998 step-increase feature is present in Environment Canada researchers' figure for the annual mean temperature anomaly for all of Canada from 1948-2018, which they obtained by gridding the AHCCD stations to 50 km-spaced grid points for the entire country (Vincent et al. 2020). Adjusting Vincent et al.'s (2020) all-Canada annual mean temperature anomaly time-series to remove the 1998 step-increase feature removes essentially all calculated warming, as is shown in Section 4.3.

In section 5, I conclude that the presence of significant apparent artifacts in the adjusted and homogenized Canadian climate data (AHCCD), and Environment Canada's unwillingness to investigate such features, including when alerted to them by researchers at other Canadian government departments or Crown corporations, are such that published claims of warming temperature trends of 1-2°C over the past several decades based on these data should be considered unreliable.

2 Data

2.1 Emails released through Access to Information

This report refers to emails between Bank of Canada and Environment Canada employees obtained in an Access to Information (ATI) request to Environment Canada, which was made by the author of this report.

The documents released pursuant to the ATI request, as well as relevant communications between the requester (Joseph Hickey) and Environment Canada's Access to Information and Privacy department, are contained in Appendix F of this report.

2.2 Temperature data used in this report

The temperature data used in this report are from Environment Canada's Adjusted and Homogenized Canadian Climate Data (AHCCD) dataset (Environment and Climate Change Canada 2024; 2025a; 2025b).

The AHCCD was created in order to conduct trend analysis of temperature and other climate variables over time periods spanning several decades (Vincent and Gullett 1999; Vincent et al. 2012; 2020; Wan et al. 2025).

Since it was first created in the 1990s, multiple different “generations” of the AHCCD have been released by Environment Canada (Gullett et al. 1992; Vincent and Gullett 1999; Vincent et al. 2012; 2020; Wan et al. 2025). The number of weather stations used to create the dataset, and the procedures used for adjusting and homogenizing the temperature time-series differ for each generation.

This report uses daily mean, maximum, and minimum temperature time-series from the 3rd generation of the AHCCD released in 2020 (Vincent et al. 2020), which contains data for 780 stations in total. As of the release of the dataset in 2020, 508 of the 780 3rd generation AHCCD stations were actively recording new observations and had records starting prior to 1990; 53 stations were actively recording new observations and had a record starting after 1990; and 219 stations were not actively recording new observations but had a record spanning more than 30 years (Vincent et al. 2020). I downloaded the 3rd generation AHCCD dataset on November 11, 2025 from Environment Canada's website (Environment and Climate Change Canada 2024).

For additional context, Environment Canada provides a downloadable PDF file (filename “Homo_Temp_Annual_Graphs_2023.pdf”) showing time-series graphs of the annual averages of daily mean, maximum, and minimum temperatures for all 780 3rd generation AHCCD stations on its website (Environment and Climate Change Canada 2024), which I accessed on November 11, 2025.

A fourth generation of the AHCCD temperature data was released in 2025 (Wan et al. 2025). Appendix C shows a comparison of temperature records for the 3rd vs the 4th generation of the AHCCD. The main results of this report apply for both the 3rd and 4th generation of the AHCCD. I downloaded the 4th generation AHCCD dataset on November 20, 2025 from the Canadian Government's Open Government portal (Environment and Climate Change Canada 2025b).

In June 2021, I emailed graphs to Environment Canada researchers showing a stepwise increase of approximately 1°C in magnitude occurring at 1998 in the annual average temperatures for a set of sixteen AHCCD stations in Eastern and Central Canada. The said sixteen AHCCD stations are listed in Table A.

Table A: The sixteen AHCCD temperature records at issue in emails with Environment Canada

Station ID	Letter	City	Province
8103201	a	Moncton	New Brunswick (NB)
8101605	b	Fredericton	New Brunswick (NB)
8104901	c	St_John	New Brunswick (NB)
8300301	d	Charlottetown	Prince Edward Island (PE)
8202251	e	Halifax	Nova Scotia (NS)
8403505	f	St_Johns	Newfoundland and Labrador (NL)
701S001	g	Quebec	Quebec (QC)
7025251	h	Montreal_Trudeau	Quebec (QC)
6105978	i	Ottawa	Ontario (ON)
6158731	j	Toronto_Pearson	Ontario (ON)
6144478	k	London	Ontario (ON)
6068145	l	Sudbury	Ontario (ON)
6048268	m	Thunder_Bay	Ontario (ON)
6032125	n	Dryden	Ontario (ON)
6034073	o	Kenora	Ontario (ON)
502S001	p	Winnipeg	Manitoba (MB)

As additional context, Appendix B of this report contains graphs for eight AHCCD stations in Western Canada, which are listed in Table B.

Table B: Additional AHCCD temperature records for stations in Western Canada

Station ID	Letter	City	Province
5010490	q	Brandon	Manitoba (MB)
4016699	r	Regina	Saskatchewan (SK)
4057165	s	Saskatoon	Saskatchewan (SK)
3034485	t	Medicine_Hat	Alberta (AB)
3031094	u	Calgary	Alberta (AB)
3012206	v	Edmonton	Alberta (AB)
1163781	w	Kamloops	British Columbia (BC)
1108380	x	Vancouver	British Columbia (BC)

The map in Figure 1 shows the sixteen Eastern and Central Canadian AHCCD stations from Table A (blue letters a-p) and the eight additional Western Canadian AHCCD stations from Table B (red letters q-x).

Figure 1: Map of Canada showing the locations of the sixteen AHCCD stations listed in Table A (a-p, blue) and the eight additional AHCCD stations listed in Table B (q-x, red).

Several of the analyses in this report use all 3rd generation AHCCD stations with sufficient data for the time-period relevant to the analysis, as described in the sections below. Maps showing the locations of all 3rd generation AHCCD stations are contained in Vincent et al. (2020).

3 Results: Apparent artifacts in the AHCCD and Environment Canada’s responses

In this section, I explain apparent artifacts in Environment Canada’s Adjusted and Homogenized Canadian Climate Data (AHCCD) that were identified by Bank of Canada staff (including myself) in 2020 and 2021, and raised with Environment Canada researchers by email.

The email exchanges, which were obtained in an Access to Information request, show how Environment Canada responded to the issues raised. Copies of the emails are included as results in this report. The full release of the Access to Information request is given in Appendix F.

3.1 Stepwise increase of approximately 1°C in magnitude occurring in 1998 in the temperature records of many Canadian AHCCD stations

3.1.1 Time-series graphs showing the 1998 step-increase feature

The AHCCD contains adjusted and homogenized time-series for the daily mean, daily maximum, and daily minimum temperatures, for many locations in Canada.

In this report, I use calendar-year (January 1 to December 31) annual averages of the AHCCD daily temperature data, to obtain the annual average of daily mean temperatures (Tmean), the annual average of daily maximum temperature (Tmax), and the annual average of daily minimum temperatures (Tmin).

Figure 2 shows the annual averages Tmean, Tmax, and Tmin for the years 1960-2020, for the sixteen AHCCD stations listed in Table A. For Halifax (Figure 2e) the x-axis ranges from 1961-2020, due to missing data for approximately half of 1960 for that station.

Figure 2 was created using the 3rd generation AHCCD dataset as downloaded on November 11, 2025 (Environment and Climate Change Canada 2024), and it is an exact reproduction of the graphs that I sent to Environment Canada researchers as an attachment to my email of June 24, 2021, which can be viewed at pages 000005-000008 of Appendix F.2.

Figure 2: Annual averages of the daily mean temperature (Tmean), daily maximum temperature (Tmax), and daily minimum temperature (Tmin), for sixteen Eastern and Central Canada AHCCD stations. All temperatures are in degrees Celsius.

As can be seen from Figure 2, many Eastern and Central Canadian AHCCD temperature records have annual mean temperature series that can be described as fluctuating around a lower plateau value from 1960-1997, followed by a stepwise increase at 1998 of approximately 1°C in magnitude up to an upper plateau value from 1998-2020 (the “1998 step-increase feature”).

Prominent examples of AHCCD stations exhibiting the 1998 step-increase feature include Moncton (Figure 2a), Fredericton (Figure 2b), Charlottetown (Figure 2d), Halifax (Figure 2e), and St. John’s (Figure 2f), which are all in Atlantic Canada (provinces of New Brunswick, Prince Edward Island, Nova Scotia, and Newfoundland and Labrador).

The 1998 step-increase feature is also evident for AHCCD stations in Quebec (Figure 2g-h) and Ontario (Figure 2i-o). For several of the AHCCD stations in Ontario (Figure 2i-o), as well as for St. John, New Brunswick (Figure 2c), the step-increase to an upper plateau beginning in 1998 is clear, while the section of the data ranging from 1960-1997 is less well-described as a plateau than in the case of the Atlantic Canada AHCCD stations mentioned above, and may be better described as a following an increasing linear trend.

For Winnipeg, Manitoba (Figure 2p), the 1998 step-increase appears to be present although less evident than for the other AHCCD stations in Figure 2.

Appendix B shows graphs of Tmean, Tmax, and Tmin for eight additional AHCCD stations in Western Canada. For these stations, the 1998 step-increase feature is not as clearly seen as for the stations in Figure 2, and appears not to be present in some cases.

In section 3.1.3, below, I apply a simple method to map the presence (or absence) of the 1998 step-increase feature, and its magnitude, across all AHCCD stations with sufficient data (approximately 300 stations).

3.1.2 Approximate magnitude of the 1998 step-increase feature for the sixteen Eastern and Central Canadian AHCCD stations listed in Table A

Figure 3 shows the graphs for Moncton from Figure 2a with added horizontal lines showing the mean of the plotted time-series for 1960-1997 (solid red line) and the mean for 1998-2020 (dashed red line). As can be seen, the stepwise increase between the two segments of the annual average temperature time-series has a magnitude of about 1°C for each of Tmean, Tmax, and Tmin.

Figure 3: The panels from Figure 2a with added horizontal lines showing the average of plotted data points for 1960-1997 (solid red line) and 1998-2020 (dashed red line). All temperatures are in degrees Celsius.

Appendix A contains graphs in the format of Figure 3, with solid and dashed red lines indicating the mean values for the 1960-1997 and 1998-2020 segments of the data, respectively, for the sixteen Eastern and Central Canadian AHCCD stations listed in Table A and shown in Figure 2.

The mean values (solid and dashed red lines, for Tmean, Tmax, and Tmin) for the sixteen Eastern and Central Canadian AHCCD stations are listed in Table C.

Table C: Mean values for first (1960-1997, except for Halifax, which uses 1961-1997) and second (1998-2020) segments of the annual average time-series for each of Tmean, Tmax, and Tmin, and the differences in the mean values of the two segments, for the sixteen Eastern and Central Canadian weather stations listed in Table A. All temperatures are in °C.

City	I: Mean of Tmean (1960- 1997)	II: Mean of Tmean (1998- 2020)	II - I	III: Mean of Tmax (1960- 1997)	IV: Mean of Tmax (1998- 2020)	IV - III	V: Mean of Tmin (1960- 1997)	VI: Mean of Tmin (1998- 2020)	VI - V
Moncton	5.38	6.43	1.05	10.37	11.37	1	0.37	1.47	1.09
Fredericton	5.67	6.54	0.87	11.09	11.74	0.65	0.24	1.32	1.08
St_John	4.92	6	1.08	9.94	11.02	1.08	-0.13	0.95	1.08
Charlottetown	5.53	6.53	1	9.59	10.57	0.98	1.47	2.48	1.02
Halifax	6.42	7.46	1.03	10.8	11.83	1.03	2.03	3.06	1.03
St_Johns	4.92	5.82	0.9	8.61	9.52	0.91	1.21	2.08	0.88
Quebec	4.45	5.23	0.78	9.12	9.97	0.85	-0.23	0.45	0.68
Montreal_ Trudeau	6.46	7.74	1.28	10.98	12.06	1.09	1.93	3.39	1.46
Ottawa	5.8	6.96	1.15	10.84	11.99	1.15	0.75	1.9	1.15

Toronto_Pearson	7.61	9.31	1.7	12.41	13.66	1.24	2.79	4.93	2.14
London	7.52	8.74	1.22	12.32	13.34	1.03	2.69	4.11	1.42
Sudbury	3.46	4.51	1.05	8.58	9.56	0.98	-1.68	-0.55	1.13
Thunder_Bay	2.82	3.58	0.77	8.5	9.57	1.07	-2.88	-2.42	0.46
Dryden	1.92	3.11	1.18	7.08	8.03	0.95	-3.26	-1.83	1.44
Kenora	2.66	3.71	1.05	7.16	7.97	0.81	-1.84	-0.56	1.28
Winnipeg	2.75	3.58	0.82	8.13	8.98	0.86	-2.63	-1.84	0.79

As can be seen from Table C, the stepwise increase between the earlier (1960-1997) and later (1998-2020) segments of the annual average temperature time-series has a magnitude of approximately 1°C in all cases. The median values of the columns showing the differences in means of the two segments for Tmean, Tmax, and Tmin (i.e. the columns labelled “II - I”, “IV - III”, and “VI - V” in Table C) are 1.05°C , 0.99°C , and 1.085°C, respectively.

3.1.3 Presence, uniqueness, and magnitude of the 1998 step-increase feature across Canada

In this section, I examine the presence and magnitude of the 1998 step-increase feature across all 3rd generation AHCCD stations with sufficient data (approximately 300 stations), and show that the 1998 step-increase feature is a uniquely large and geographically widespread discontinuity in the AHCCD dataset.

The said examination is done using distributions of two quantities defined below that can be calculated from any one of the annual average temperature time series Tmean, Tmax, or Tmin, for a particular AHCCD station. In the following definitions, I use T to mean any of Tmean, Tmax, or Tmin.

The first quantity, Δ_s , is the difference in the averages of T taken over the years corresponding to two windows on either side of a test break year. The first window, w_1 , contains the N years prior to the test break year, and the second window, w_2 , contains the test break year itself and the subsequent N-1 years. For example, for the break year 1998, with N = 5, Δ_s is calculated by subtracting the average of T taken over the years 1993-1997 from the average of T taken over the years 1998-2002.

Δ_s is a rough measure of the size of a step occurring at the corresponding test break year. When Δ_s is close to zero, for a particular choice of T, AHCCD station, and test break year, then there is no discernible step for the given time-series at the test break year. When Δ_s is large and negative, there is potentially a step downwards in the temperature record, and when Δ_s is large and positive, there is potentially a step upwards in the temperature record.

To better gauge whether a large absolute value of Δ_s corresponds to a step that is discernible with respect to the year-to-year fluctuations in T, one can normalize Δ_s by the standard deviations of T for each of the windows w_1 and w_2 . Therefore, the second quantity used in this section, S_r , is calculated as follows:

$$S_r = \Delta_s / ((\sigma_{w1} + \sigma_{w2})/2), \quad (1)$$

where σ_{w1} is the standard deviation of T over the first window, w_1 , and σ_{w2} is the standard deviation of T over the second window, w_2 .

S_r is thus the difference in averages of T for the two windows centered on the break year (Δ_s), scaled by the average of the two standard deviations σ_{w1} and σ_{w2} .

For a given test break year (“break year” for short), both Δ_s and S_r can be calculated for all AHCCD records with sufficient data, and then the distributions of Δ_s and S_r can be examined as a function of break year. For the figures in this section, an AHCCD station was considered to have sufficient data if its record for T had at least 350 days of non-missing daily data for each of the years in w_1 and w_2 .

The right panel of Figure 4 shows distributions of Δ_s , over all usable AHCCD stations across Canada, for a selection of break years, with $N=5$, for $T=T_{\text{mean}}$. As can be seen, the distribution for the break year 1998 (black) stands out, due to the high frequency of AHCCD records with $\Delta_s > 1$, suggesting geographically widespread presence of a large discontinuity across AHCCD stations for the break year 1998. The other distributions shown in the right panel of Figure 4 are centered on $\Delta_s = 0$, showing that there are no geographically widespread discontinuities for the corresponding break years.

Figure 4: Left panel: Mean (μ), standard deviation (σ), median, and mode (all in units of $^{\circ}\text{C}$) of the distribution of Δ_s calculated using Tmean, as a function of break year. The dashed vertical line indicates 1998. Right panel: distributions of Δ_s shown for selected break years. Two five-year windows, were used, with the break year being the first year of the later five-year window. Distributions use all 3rd generation AHCCD stations with sufficient data for the calculation of Δ_s , for each given break year.

The left panel of Figure 4 shows the mean (μ), standard deviation (σ), median, and mode (histogram bin value with the highest frequency) (all in units of $^{\circ}\text{C}$), for the distributions of Δ_s calculated for Tmean with $N=5$, for all break years from 1948 to 2019. The number of AHCCD stations with sufficient data depends on the break year, and is typically around 300 stations.

As can be seen from the left panel of Figure 4, the break year 1998 stands out (with 1997) as having the largest values of μ , median, and mode among all break years, and 1998 (with 1997) is the only break year with μ , median, and mode values greater than 1°C in magnitude.

Figure 5 shows a map of values of Δ_s for Tmean with $N=5$ for the break year 1998, for all AHCCD stations across Canada with sufficient data (302 stations). Each circle is centered on an AHCCD station, and the radius of the circle is proportional to Δ_s . AHCCD stations with blue circles have $\Delta_s < 0$, while black circles correspond to $0 \leq \Delta_s \leq 1$, and red circles correspond to $\Delta_s > 1$ ($^{\circ}\text{C}$ magnitude).

Tmean
 Δ_S for $w_1 = 1993-1997$ and $w_2 = 1998-2002$
 (302 stations with sufficient data)

Figure 5: Map showing Δ_S calculated using Tmean, for the break year 1998 with two five-year windows (1993-1997 and 1998-2002) ($N = 5$) for the 302 3rd generation AHCCD stations with sufficient data. Circle radius is proportional to the absolute value of Δ_S . Circle colour indicates Δ_S ranges as follows: blue: $\Delta_S < 0$; black: $0 \leq \Delta_S \leq 1$; red: $\Delta_S > 1$ ($^{\circ}\text{C}$ magnitude). Moncton, NB ($\Delta_S = 1.35$) is indicated with a green circle, for reference.

As can be seen from Figure 5, many AHCCD records across Canada have $\Delta_S > 1$ (red circles), covering essentially all of Eastern and Central Canada, and extending well into the Western part of the country. The main exceptions (black and blue circles) are found in British Columbia (west coast province), part of Alberta (to the east of British Columbia), and for some stations in the north of the country.

Figure 6 shows similar results to Figure 4, here for the dimensionless quantity S_r .

Figure 6: Left panel: Mean (μ), standard deviation (σ), median, and mode (all dimensionless) of the distribution of S_r calculated using Tmean, as a function of break year. The dashed vertical line indicates 1998. Right panel: distributions of S_r shown for selected break years. Two five-year windows, were used, with the break year being the first year of the later five-year window. Distributions use all 3rd generation AHCCD stations with sufficient data for the calculation of S_r , for each given break year.

As was the case in Figure 4, Figure 6 shows that 1998 is unique in being a year with many AHCCD records having large stepwise discontinuities in the annual average Tmean, here after normalizing using the average of the standard deviations of the data on either side of the break (Eq. 1). The distribution of S_r in the right panel of Figure 6 shows that many S_r values for the break year 1998 have values greater than two, demonstrating that a step magnitude Δ_s more than twice as large as the typical year-to-year fluctuations in Tmean in the years around the break are found for many AHCCD stations, for the break year 1998.

Figure 7 shows a map of S_r for Tmean with $N=5$, for break year 1998, for all AHCCD stations across Canada with sufficient data (302 stations).

Tmean
 S_r for $w_1 = 1993-1997$ and $w_2 = 1998-2002$
 (302 stations with sufficient data)

Figure 7: Map showing S_r calculated using Tmean, for the break year 1998 with two five-year windows (1993-1997 and 1998-2002) for the 302 3rd generation AHCCD stations with sufficient data. Circle radius is proportional to the absolute value of S_r . Circle colour indicates S_r ranges as follows: blue: $S_r < 0$; black: $0 \leq S_r \leq 1$; red: $S_r > 1$. Moncton, NB ($S_r = 2.74$) is indicated with a green circle, for reference.

In Figure 7, AHCCD stations with $S_r < 0$ are coloured blue, while black indicates $0 \leq S_r \leq 1$, and red indicates $S_r > 1$. The AHCCD records with the largest stepwise increases at 1998 are located in Eastern and Central Canada (including the stations listed in Table A), and there are many records with discernible steps at 1998 in the Prairies (provinces of Manitoba, Saskatchewan, and Alberta) and the north of the country. British Columbia remains the main outlier, with most of its AHCCD stations having no discernible steps at 1998.

The results shown in this section are robust to different choices of T and N, as shown in the figures in Appendix D.

3.1.4 Temperature trends post-1998

If anything, the two-decade trend in annual average temperature series for many AHCCD stations is negative post-1998. This can be seen from the map in Figure 8, which shows temperature trends for Tmean over the period 1998-2018 for AHCCD stations with sufficient data (149 stations). The trend calculations are explained below.

Trend in Tmean for period 1998-2018 (linear least squares fit)

Figure 8: Map of trend in Tmean over the period 1998-2018, for the 3rd generation AHCCD stations with sufficient data, calculated using linear least-squares fitting. Circle radius is proportional to the absolute value of the trend. Blue circles correspond to negative trends (trend < 0) and red circles to positive trends (trend > 0).

In Figure 8, the trend for a particular Tmean record is equal to the slope ($^{\circ}\text{C}/\text{year}$) from a linear least-squares fit to its data for 1998-2018, times 21 years. An AHCCD station was considered to have sufficient data if its record had at least 350 days of non-missing daily data per year for every year from 1998-2018. Approximately two thirds of the AHCCD records with sufficient data have negative trends for 1998-2018 using linear least-squares fitting.

As an alternative, the method primarily applied by Environment Canada researchers to estimate trends from the AHCCD data and assess their statistical significance is the slope estimation method of Sen (1968) with the Zhang et al. (2000) implementation of the non-parametric

Kendall's tau test (Kendall 1955). I applied this methodology using the “zyp” software package for R (Bronaugh et al. 2023) to the same AHCCD records used to make Figure 8 (149 stations), and the result is shown in Figure 9.

Trend in Tmean for period 1998-2018 (method of Sen/Zhang, sig. level $\alpha = 0.05$)

Figure 9: Map of trend in Tmean over the period 1998-2018, for 3rd generation AHCCD stations with sufficient data, calculated using the method of Sen (1968). “X” marks AHCCD stations with p values greater than 0.05 using the Zhang et al. (2000) implementation of the non-parametric Kendall’s tau test. For AHCCD stations with $p < 0.05$ (only Inuvik, Northwest Territories, and Pitt Meadows, British Columbia, in this figure), the circle radius is proportional to the absolute value of the trend. Blue symbols correspond to negative values (trend < 0) and red symbols to positive values (trend > 0).

In Figure 9, a blue “X” indicates a negative trend value that is statistically insignificant at the significance threshold $\alpha = 0.05$ (i.e. the p value for the trend is greater than 0.05, such that the

null hypothesis of zero slope is not rejected). A red “X” indicates a positive trend value that is statistically insignificant. Red circles are used to indicate two positive trends with $p < 0.05$, and the magnitude of the trend is proportional to the circle radius.

As can be seen from Figure 9, almost all of the AHCCD stations with sufficient data have statistically insignificant trends for 1998-2018, and approximately half of the trends are negative for 1998-2018, according to the Sen/Zhang methodology.

Graphs in the format of Figures 8 and 9 for the pre-step periods 1960-1997 and 1977-1997 are included in Appendix E, and show that many AHCCD stations have essentially zero slope over these two multi-decade time periods leading up to the 1998 step-increase feature.

3.2 Emails exchanged with Environment Canada about the 1998 step-increase feature

3.2.1 First email exchange alerting Environment Canada researchers to the presence of the 1998 step-increase feature

While working on a project involving the AHCCD as a data scientist at the Bank of Canada, I sent the graphs shown in Figure 2 of this report to Environment Canada researchers by email on June 24, 2021, and asked for assistance understanding the origin of the 1998 step-increase feature, pointing out that it appeared to be an artifact.

My June 24, 2021 email is contained in pages 000021-000023 of Appendix F.2 of this report, and the graphs that were attached to my June 24, 2021 email are shown on pages 000005-000008 of Appendix F.2 of this report.

The text of my June 24, 2021 email to Environment Canada researchers Lucie A. Vincent, Megan Hartwell, and Xiaolan Wang is as follows:

From: Joseph Hickey <JHickey@bank-banque-canada.ca>
Sent: June 24, 2021 8:49 AM
To: Vincent, Lucie (EC) <lucie.vincent@canada.ca>; Hartwell, Megan (EC) <megan.hartwell@canada.ca>; Wang, Xiaolan (EC) <xiaolan.wang@canada.ca>
Cc: Tatjana Dahlhaus <tdahlhaus@bank-banque-canada.ca>
Subject: Bank of Canada's use of the 3rd Gen. AHCCD

Category/Catégorie: Non-Sensitive/Non-Délicat

Dear Drs. Vincent, Hartwell, and Wang,

The Bank of Canada is using Environment and Climate Change Canada's 3rd Generation Adjusted and Homogenized Canadian Climate Data (AHCCD) in its policy and research work. I've been asked to write to you in the hope of clarifying a concern we have about the data.

While working with the AHCCD, we noticed a stepwise shift upwards of about 1 degree Celsius in magnitude occurring at around 1998 in the temperature records for several stations. The shift appears in plots of the yearly average of the AHCCD daily mean, max, or min temperature time-series. The same shift is also present in the raw data.

We would interpret that the sharpness in time and the magnitude of the shift are such that it must be of non-climatic origin. Also, I note that the shift occurs at a time when many manual weather stations were being replaced with automatic stations in Canada.

The magnitude of the shift is such that it could be the cause of all or most of the trend values that are extracted from this data by various researchers.

I explain these observations in more detail below, including several graphs I have made from the AHCCD data, which are in the attachment to this email.

We would appreciate any clarifications or guidance you might provide in understanding this aspect of the data, which appears to be an artifact.

Sincerely,

Joseph

--

Joseph Hickey, PhD

Data Scientist | Scientifique des données

Canadian Economic Analysis | Analyses de l'économie canadienne

Bank of Canada | Banque du Canada

jhickey@bank-banque-canada.ca

Yearly-averaged temperature plots for several stations in Eastern Canada

I have attached a PDF file to this email containing graphs of yearly-averaged temperature time-series for several AHCCD stations. Each row of graphs shows the data for a particular AHCCD station. In each row, the left graph shows the yearly-average of Tmean, and the centre and right graphs show the yearly-average of Tmax and Tmin, respectively. The Tmax, Tmin, and Tmean records are in degrees Celsius, and $Tmean = (Tmax + Tmin)/2$.

As an example, the top row of graphs in the attachment shows the yearly-averaged time series for Moncton. The AHCCD time-series for Moncton were constructed by joining a record from a downtown station (station ID: 8103100) spanning 1898-1939 with a record from the Moncton

Airport (station ID: 8103200) spanning 1940-2012 and with a record from NavCan (station ID: 8103201) spanning 2012-2018 (Vincent et al., 2020). For Moncton, the AHCCD spreadsheet "Homog_max_temp_Inhomog_Causes.xls" (downloaded from the link here) indicates that an adjustment was made to the Tmax record in 1940 and that the potential cause was "Stations joined". The AHCCD spreadsheet "Homog_min_temp_Inhomog_Causes.xls" indicates that adjustments were made to the Tmin record at 1926, 1940, and 1961, with potential causes of "Reloc in 1926 to pumping station", "Stations joined", and "Change in obs time", respectively. These adjustments for Moncton are described further in Vincent et al. (2020). The AHCCD data for Moncton therefore contains no linking or homogenization adjustments for the period between 1961 and 2012.

As can be seen from the top row of plots in my attachment, the yearly-averaged Tmean, Tmax, and Tmin time-series for Moncton undergo an upward shift approximately 1 degree Celsius in magnitude at about 1998. Similar step-increase features at about 1998 are present in many other stations, as can be seen in my attachment. Additionally, for Moncton and some of the other stations in my attachment, the data segments for 1960-1997 and 1999-2020 appear to have roughly no trend.

Replacement of manual stations with automatic stations in 1992-2000

Vincent et al. (2020, at pg. 4) state that many stations in Canada underwent a change from manual to automatic observations between 1992 and 2000. Milewska and Vincent (2016, at pg. 34) give some additional information, as follows:

"In order to reduce the dependence of the RCS [reference climate station] network on third parties, Environment Canada initiated a climate network modernization project in 1996 (Yip et al., personal communication, 1999), in which continuity of records at vulnerable RCS stations was ensured through carefully managed systematic automation of the measurement programs. If no suitable nearby RCS replacement station was available, locations that were perceived at risk of closure in the future were automated using a tested, uniformly managed, standardized set of instruments. Some sites had already been automated prior to 1996 because more widespread automation aimed at streamlining operations had begun in the early 1990s. In 1998, a subset of 72 RCS stations was designated a part of Global Climate Observing System (Goodrich & Westermeyer, 2012) Surface Network (GSN). During the following years the list of RCS and GSN stations was further refined, and new automated stations were added in the North where no stations had previously existed."

I do not have information that would allow me to know whether or not the specific stations for which I have shown graphs in my attachment converted from manual to automatic during this time period, but this information may be contained in the "metadata" for specific stations in the Canadian Climate Data Archives of Environment and Climate Change Canada.

Effect of a 1-degree upward shift on temperature trend

In yearly data spanning 1960-2019, just having a stepwise shift at 1998 is on its own enough to cause a rise equal to about 1.4 times the magnitude of the step, in a fit of a simple linear model. A rise of 1.4 (corresponding to a step of size 1 degree Celsius) is roughly equal to the trend values extracted from the AHCCD temperature data for many stations over 1960-2019, which are typically between 1-2 degrees in magnitude.

References

E.J. Milewska and L.A. Vincent, "Preserving continuity of long-term daily maximum and minimum temperature observations with automation of reference climate stations using overlapping data and meteorological conditions", *Atmosphere-Ocean*, 54 (2016) 32-47.

L.A. Vincent, M.M. Hartwell, and X.L. Wang, "A third generation of homogenized temperature for trend analysis and monitoring changes in Canada's climate", *Atmosphere-Ocean*, iFirst article (2020) 1-19.

Environment Canada Research Climatologist Lucie A. Vincent responded to me in emails dated June 24 and 25, 2021 (pages 000020-000021 of Appendix F.2):

From: Vincent, Lucie (EC)
Sent: June 24, 2021 11:47 AM
To: 'Joseph Hickey' <JHickey@bank-banque-canada.ca>; Hartwell, Megan (EC) <megan.hartwell@canada.ca>; Wang, Xiaolan (EC) <xiaolan.wang@canada.ca>
Cc: Tatjana Dahlhaus <tdahlhaus@bank-banque-canada.ca>
Subject: RE: Bank of Canada's use of the 3rd Gen. AHCCD

Hi Joseph,

Thank you for your enquiry. We will look into this issue and let you know. For now, we think that this issue is not related to the replacement of manual weather stations by automatic stations. But we will investigate this further.

We appreciate your comments and questions. Thank you.

Lucie

From: Vincent, Lucie (EC) <lucie.vincent@canada.ca>

Sent: June 25, 2021 2:53 PM

To: Joseph Hickey <JHickey@bank-banque-canada.ca>

Cc: Hartwell, Megan (EC) <megan.hartwell@canada.ca>; Wang, Xiaolan (EC) <xiaolan.wang@canada.ca>; Carou, Silvina (EC) <silvina.carou@canada.ca>

Subject: {External} FW: Bank of Canada's use of the 3rd Gen. AHCCD

Hi Joseph,

I would like to confirm that the shift visually detected around 1998 in the time series of the annual mean temperature for the stations attached are not due to automation.

I quickly checked the metadata for some of the stations and I was not able to retrieve a date of change from manual to automated observations around 1998. Automation has been introduced gradually in Canada, from the early 1990s to the 2000s. In our studies, no systematic biases were found in daily temperature as result of automation as far as the instrumental systems were concerned. Based on a limited number of pair-sites, the Automatic Weather Observing System (AWOS) have shown slightly warmer temperatures, up to 0.2°C at some locations, due to unaspirated Stevenson screens, but now all screens are properly ventilated and they have been properly ventilated since many years.

Looking at temperatures from around the globe, we can see that the average temperature of the past decade (2011-2020) is definitively warmer than the previous decade (2001-2010), which is also warmer than the previous one (1991-2000). The results of our studies regarding the temperature homogenization and trends are in agreement with the findings of other regions from around the globe.

I hope that this helps. Thank you for your interest in our work.

Lucie

Lucie A. Vincent

Research Climatologist / Climatologue chercheur

Climate Research Division / Division de la recherche climatique

Science and Technology Branch / Direction générale de la science et technologie

Environment and Climate Change Canada / Environnement et Changement climatique Canada

4905 Dufferin Street / 4905 rue Dufferin

Toronto, Ontario, Canada, M3H 5T4

Telephone / Téléphone : 416-739-4337

Facsimile / Télécopieur : 416-739-5700

Email / Courriel: Lucie.Vincent@canada.ca

I followed up with a further email to Lucie Vincent in July 2021, arguing that stepwise increases in temperature time-series such as the 1998 step-increase feature seen in Figure 2 of this report are always considered to be of non-climatic origin in the scientific literature. These points are explained in section 3.2.2, below.

3.2.2 Second email exchange regarding the non-climatic origin of the 1998 step-increase feature and possible causal factors

Large abrupt shifts in temperature records — such as those seen for many of the stations in Figure 2 of this report — are always considered to be non-climatic and must be investigated, and corrected for, if possible. Not to mention that in the present case a large number of said large shifts are of the same magnitude and year-wise synchronous (1998) across most of Canada.

I made this point in an email to Environment Canada researcher Lucie A. Vincent sent on July 5, 2021.

My July 5, 2021 email to Lucie Vincent contained a detailed appendix quoting and citing many statements from the scientific literature confirming the need to address both sharp discontinuities and gradual biases in temperature time-series data.

The appendix of my July 5, 2021 email also contained three tables showing key examples of observational and experimental studies that have attempted to quantify the degree to which certain non-climatic factors can skew measurements of surface air temperature. I grouped the said factors into the following categories:

- a) changes in land use / land cover (LULC) characteristics in the environment surrounding the instruments;
- b) changes to the instruments themselves; and
- c) changes in observation or measurement procedures.

My email of July 5, 2021 and its appendix were included in the Access to Information release (pages 000010-000020 of Appendix F.2 of this report), and read as follows:

<p>From: Joseph Hickey Sent: July 5, 2021 8:17 AM To: 'Vincent, Lucie (EC)' <lucie.vincent@canada.ca> Cc: Hartwell, Megan (EC) <megan.hartwell@canada.ca>; Wang, Xiaolan (EC) <xiaolan.wang@canada.ca>; Carou, Silvina (EC) <silvina.carou@canada.ca>; Tatjana Dahlhaus <tdahlhaus@bank-banque-canada.ca> Subject: RE: Bank of Canada's use of the 3rd Gen. AHCCD</p>
--

Dear Dr. Vincent,

Thank you for your email of June 25 responding to my inquiry about whether instrument automation could have caused a discontinuity occurring at around 1998 in the temperature records of many weather stations in Eastern Canada.

I understand that, in your quick check of the metadata for several stations, you did not retrieve a date of change from manual to automated observations around 1998. However, I would like to determine the cause of the discontinuity, whatever the cause might be.

In the appendix to this email (below), I argue that one must conclude that such a large abrupt shift can only be non-climatic. This is a well-established point, regarding yearly-averaged weather station temperature records. I've organized the appendix into sections as follows:

- 1) Large abrupt shifts in temperature records are always considered to be non-climatic
- 2) Examples of quantified effects of non-climatic changes on measured temperature
 - a) Table 1: Effect of land use / land cover (LULC) changes
 - b) Table 2: Effect of instrumentation changes
 - c) Table 3: Effect of changes to observation methodology or procedures
- 3) Conclusion
- 4) List of References

The appendix shows that there are several known physical causes of artifacts affecting surface air temperature measurements that can disrupt or bias a temperature record. Many such circumstances can produce permanent shifts in mean annual temperature that can have magnitudes of the order of 1°C.

We would, therefore, very much appreciate your help in confirming that the discontinuity at around 1998 is non-climatic and, if possible, in determining its likely actual cause.

Sincerely,

Joseph

--

Joseph Hickey, PhD

Data Scientist | Scientifique des données

Canadian Economic Analysis | Analyses de l'économie canadienne

Bank of Canada | Banque du Canada

234 rue Wellington Street, Ottawa ON K1A 0G9

Telephone | Téléphone : 613-782-7257

jhickey@bank-banque-canada.ca

Appendix

Section 1. Large abrupt shifts in temperature records are always considered to be non-climatic

Large abrupt shifts in temperature records are always considered to be non-climatic and must be investigated, and corrected for, if possible. The scientific literature has statements to this effect, such as the following.

Peterson et al. (1998), "Homogeneity adjustments of in situ atmospheric climate data: A review", *Int. J. Climatol.* 18:1493-1517

"Unfortunately, most long-term climatological time series have been affected by a number of non-climatic factors that make these data unrepresentative of the actual climate variation occurring over time. These factors include changes in: instruments, observing practices, station locations, formulae used to calculate means, and station environment (Jones et al., 1985; Karl and Williams, 1987; Gullett et al., 1990; Heino, 1994). **Some changes cause sharp discontinuities while other changes, particularly change in the environment around the station, can cause gradual biases in the data.** All of these inhomogeneities can bias a time series and lead to misinterpretations of the studied climate. It is important, therefore, to remove the inhomogeneities or at least determine the possible error they may cause."

Peterson & Easterling (1994), "Creation of homogeneous composite climatological reference series", *Int. J. Climatol.* 14:671-679

"Many of the research problems facing climatologists today, such as global climate change, require long homogeneous time series: time series where variations are caused only by variations of weather and climate (Conrad and Pollock, 1950). **However, it is rare to find long time series that do not have some artificial changes in their statistical characteristics.** Using data that have not been adjusted adequately for inhomogeneities can often lead to erroneous conclusions because the climate-change signal can be obscured easily or enhanced artificially by discontinuities in the data. For example, Hansen and Lebedeffs (1988) analysis of global surface-temperature trends indicates considerable warming in the 1980s around St Helena Island (16°S, 6°W). However, much of this 'warming' was actually due to an inhomogeneity in the St Helena Island time series caused by the station moving to a lower elevation (P. Michaels, pers. Comm., 1992)."

Inhomogeneities in time series arise either due to abrupt discontinuities or to effects that gradually increase over time. **Abrupt discontinuities occur as a result of instrument and exposure changes, station moves, and changes in calculation procedures for time-averaged values.** Inhomogeneities that occur as a gradually increasing effect generally develop as a result of a change in the environment surrounding a station, such as urbanization, or a gradual change in either the instrument calibration or the physical characteristics of the instrument apparatus (e.g. yellowing of a white plastic instrument shelter (Quale et al., 1991)).”

Easterling & Peterson (1995), “A new method for detecting undocumented discontinuities in climatological time series”, *Int. J. Climatol.* 15:369-377

“It is impossible to verify that a climatological time series is truly homogeneous, and it is very rare to find a long climatological time series that is even homogeneous relative to surrounding stations. Furthermore, even if there are accompanying metadata, in the form of station histories, that are used to make data adjustments for homogenization purposes, the potential still exists that some undocumented station change has affected the statistical characteristics of the time series. Station history files are often incomplete and may not routinely document changes that can cause a discontinuity. For example, Easterling and Peterson (1992) examined a number of techniques for detecting discontinuities, and using data from the United States Historical Climatology Network (USHCN, Karl et al., 1990) demonstrated that discontinuities can be identified for such instances as replacing a thermometer with a new one of the same model, or simply calibrating the instrument.”

Jones et al. (1986), “Northern hemisphere surface air temperature variations: 1851-1984”, *J. Clim. App. Meteor.* 25:161-179

“It has long been known that the basic source of long term station air temperature records (WWR) contains many station records that are not homogeneous (i.e., they contain changes that result from nonclimatic factors). For example, values for individual months can be misspelled, misprinted or simply incorrect. More serious errors may arise from station moves, changes in observation times and the effects of environmental changes around the station. **These factors may cause spurious discontinuities and trends that are not the result of climatic change and which may obscure or distort any climate-related change.**”

Zurbenko et al. (1996), “Detecting discontinuities in time series of upper-air data: Development and demonstration of an adaptive filter technique”, *J. Climate* 9:3548-3560
[Here, referring to upper-air temperature data]

“Unfortunately, these data contain systematic errors caused by changes in instruments, data acquisition procedures, etc. It is essential that systematic errors be identified and/or removed before these data can be used confidently in the context of greenhouse-gas-induced climate modification.”

(...)

“The detection of abrupt changes due to instrumentation or data reduction procedures is complicated by the nature of daily temperature and humidity data. The time series of upper-air data can be characterized as high-frequency change combined with low-frequency seasonal and trend components. The seasonal components vary from year to year and, in the presence of the high-frequency component, are difficult to separate from abrupt discontinuities using parametric methods. **In addressing this problem we presume that changes in data due to instrument change are characterized by their abrupt and persistent nature. This behavior is contrasted with long-term climate or short-term weather systems.”**

The above passage emphasizes the abrupt and persistent nature of a non-climatic inhomogeneity, in contrast to long-term (decadal or longer) climate or short-term (minutes, hours, days) weather systems. This is relevant to the shift at around 1998 at Eastern Canada stations because it occurs between two regimes of twenty or more years with roughly zero trend, for many stations.

Lastly, in Vincent & Gullett (1999) shifts greater than 0.6 degrees Celsius were assumed to be non-climatic and therefore needing adjustment:

Vincent & Gullett (1999), “Canadian historical and homogeneous temperature datasets for climate change analysis”, *Int. J. Climatol.* 19:1375-1388

“The following rule was therefore implemented: **steps greater than 0.6°C, identified in the annual series, are always adjusted regardless of the presence or lack of supporting station history**; steps between 0.4 and 0.6°C are adjusted only with supporting station history; and steps less than 0.4°C are not adjusted since they are not often adequately identified by this or any other technique.

(...)

Figure 3 illustrates a typical station homogeneity assessment and adjustment situation. The annual mean minimum temperatures for Saint John, NB, are tested for homogeneity for the period 1895–1995. The series shows a

decreasing linear trend of 2.4°C:101 years before adjustment (Figure 3(a)). Four steps are clearly identified by the procedure (Figure 3(b)). The step in 1961 results from the change of observing window which produced a bias in the minimum temperature in 1961 at principal stations (described in the following section); the step in 1950 is associated with a site relocation with a 13-m increase in elevation; the step in 1947 is caused by the joining of two segments, Saint John and Saint John A in 1947; and finally the step in 1915 is caused by another site relocation with an increase in elevation of 9 m in 1914. **All of these steps are large enough to be adjusted with confidence without metadata support**, however, supporting history information was readily available to determine their causes. The adjusted series for Saint John, NB, shows a temperature increase of 0.2°C:101 years (Figure 3(c)), compared to a decrease of 2.4°C:101 years in the unadjusted series. Increasing linear trends of about this magnitude are also observed at neighbouring stations, and it is concluded that the adjusted series reflects more closely the temperature variations of the area.”

Section 2: Examples of quantified effects of non-climatic changes on measured temperature

As noted in the passages quoted in Section 1, there are many factors that could introduce non-climatic inhomogeneities into a temperature record. Some of these factors have been quantitatively studied in experiments or observational studies. The following tables list several key examples of studies that have quantified the effect on surface air temperature of changes to:

- a) Land use / land cover (LULC) characteristics in the environment surrounding the instruments (Table 1);
- b) The instruments themselves (Table 2);
- c) Observation or measurement procedures (Table 3).

Note that, in Table 1, some of the cited studies report the impact of environmental changes that occurred gradually. However, if the same environmental changes were to be implemented abruptly, they would necessarily give rise to an abrupt change in the temperature record. My purpose in presenting the references in Tables 1-3 is to show the magnitude of the impact of the different types of changes. The changes themselves can be abrupt even if they were gradual in the specific studies I’ve cited.

Table 1: Examples of quantified effect of land use / land cover (LULC) changes on surface air temperature

Type of LULC change	Proposed mechanisms by which change affects surface air temp.	Examples of quantified effect of change on surface air temp.
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		<p>Exp = Experimental study Obs = Observational study</p>
Addition of buildings	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Reduction of sky-view factor - Shelter from wind - Shade - Increase of surface roughness affecting air flow 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Up to 1.2°C (0.5°C) increase in monthly mean minimum (maximum) at sheltered (“Test1”) site compared to reference site. (Brandsma, 2011) [Exp] - Up to 0.8°C mean difference in temperature between site closest to and furthest from built environment. (Leeper et al., 2019) [Exp] - 0.31°C (0.09°C) increase in minimum (maximum) temperature after local change to built environment (addition of building and parking lot, rerouted road) in early 2013 at Kingston, RI Climate Reference Network station. (Leeper et al., 2019) [Obs]
Addition of pavement (parking lots, runways, roads, etc.)	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Different thermal conductivity and heat capacity than natural cover types like soil, sand, or grassland - Advection (horizontal movement of air warmed by pavement) - Change of albedo compared to natural cover, and pavement albedo changes as it ages from black to grey - Reduction of evaporating surfaces thus elevating sensible heating 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - 0.3°C (0.12°C) mean difference of daily minimum (maximum) temperature between site closest to and furthest from an asphalt car road at temperature measurement height of 2m. (Coppa et al., 2021) [Exp] - 0.2-0.4°C (0.1°C) mean difference of temperature between leeward and windward sides of an asphalt car road at temperature measurement height of 0.5m (1.5m). (Kumamoto et al., 2013) [Exp]
Addition of trees, shrubs, bushes	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Reduction of sky-view factor - Shelter from wind - Shade - Increase of surface roughness affecting air flow 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Up to 0.6°C (0.4°C) decrease (increase) in monthly mean minimum (maximum) at test (“DB260”) site near trees compared to reference site. (Brandsma, 2011) [Exp] - Mean nighttime air temperature substantially higher (>2°C) at shrubland site vs. grassland site in New Mexico

		desert. (He et al., 2010) [Obs]
Changes to irrigation practices	- Irrigation increases soil moisture thus less sensible energy available for near surface warming	- “Results show notably cooler temperatures over irrigated areas. For example, mean maximum growing season temperature at irrigated Alliance was 0.64°C and 1.65°C cooler compared to non-irrigated Halsey during pre- and post-1945 period, respectively.” (Mahmood et al., 2006) [Obs] - “During [the July experimental period], on average, the mean daily temperature over irrigated areas was reduced by -0.69°C because of increased physical evaporation from soils and transpiration from crops.” (Rappin et al., 2021) [Exp]
Growth of nearby urban area (“urban heat island effect”)	- Many factors affecting radiative and thermal properties of the ground and surface, and air movement, etc. due to replacing natural environment with streets, buildings, etc. (Oke, 2010).	- 0.9°C increase over 80 years due to growth of local urban settlement toward the temperature sensor at Urbana, IL. (Changnon & Kunkel, 2006) [Obs] - 0.6°C increase over 45 years in urban development area of Vienna (Bohm, 1998). [Obs]

Table 2: Examples of quantified effect of instrumentation changes on surface air temperature

Type of instrumentation change	Proposed mechanisms by which change affects surface air temp.	Examples of quantified effect of change on surface air temp. Exp = Experimental study Obs = Observational study
Change from liquid-in-glass to resistance thermometers	- Thermometer “drift” in resistance thermometers (e.g. due to changes in the resistance-temperature relationship due to different thermal expansion coefficients of the sensing element and the substrate	- “The evaluated drift resulted in the order of 0.4°C, over 30 months of field measurements (figure 6). The exposure to low temperature and humidity showed similar values (figure 7).” (Merlone, 2021) [Exp] - “During the past five years, the National Weather Service (NWS) has replaced over

	<p>on which it is mounted) (Berry, 1982)</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Column separations in liquid-in-glass thermometers causing erroneously high maximum and low minimum readings (Quayle et al., 1991) - Changes to the surroundings of the thermometer (such as the screen) when the thermometer is replaced (Quayle et al., 1991) 	<p>half of its liquid-in-glass maximum and minimum thermometers in wooden Cotton Region Shelters (CRSs) with thermistor-based Maximum-Minimum Temperature Systems (MMTSs) housed in smaller plastic shelters. Analyses of data from 424 (of the 3300) MMTS stations and 675 CRS stations show that a mean daily minimum temperature change of roughly +0.3°C, a mean daily maximum temperature change of -0.4°C, and a change in average temperature of -0.1 °C were introduced as a result of the new instrumentation.” (Quayle et al., 1991) [Obs]</p>
Change from manual to automatic weather stations	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Self-heating of thermometer from electrical components inside the instrument shelter - Changes to the surroundings of the thermometer (such as the screen) when the thermometer is replaced 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - “Self-heating in automatic weather stations originates not only from the temperature sensor itself but also from the electrical components housed together within. [...] In the study, the measured difference from the initial measured temperature was measured up to +0.32°C for currents compatible with modern dataloggers.” (Merlone, 2021) [Exp] - “The reported differences between the automatic and the manual measurements in side by side comparisons vary between ~0.1°C (Trewin, 2010) to up to 3°C (Bares & Mozny, 2014) [Exp] with the largest differences recorded on windless sunny days.” (Tsinko, 2016)
Change of screen type: adequacy of radiation shielding	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Whether screen properly shields radiation, including “back-radiation” reflected from the ground 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - “The experiment involved pairs of identical thermometers and shields, as commercially provided by manufacturers, including aspirated or naturally ventilated shields. Of the couples of identical sensors, one was positioned 2 m above snow covered soil and the other 2 m above soil without presence of snow in the same site and in close vicinity, to guarantee same meteorological exposure [...] The effect under investigation was

		<p>based on evaluating the differences among each couple of identical sensors. This was due to the overheating of the sensor above the snow, caused by the reflected radiation, hitting the shield from below. Results showed different amount of overheating, among the different typologies of instruments, ranging from about 0.5°C up to even 2.5°C, as shown in figure 5. As expected, the effect is evident only in daytime hours, while in the night the readings distribution is coherent with the overall calibration uncertainties of the various sensors.” (Merlone, 2021) [Exp]</p> <p>- “For the naturally ventilated screens/shields, a maximum positive Tdev of +3.4°C for AV-040(N) is seen from the influence of global solar radiation.” (Aoshima et al., 2010) [Exp]</p> <p>- “From our work, we can conclude that the temperature shift a [sic] average is of magnitude 0°C to +0.7°C when considering change in radiation shield type. [...] In case of temperature maximums, the shift can be up to +1.6°C in days with high global radiation (...)” (Bartokova et al., 2014) [Exp]</p>
<p>Change of screen type: aging and repainting/repair</p>	<p>- Aging of screen exterior (e.g. yellowing of plastic or loss of paint), or repainting or repairing screen exterior following weathering. (Screen exterior should be highly reflective to prevent radiative warming of air passing over screen material before arriving at thermometer.)</p>	<p>- “Lopardo et al. (2014) [Exp] looked at the age of AWS [automatic weather station] screens and found that the wearing off of the reflective coating can lead to significant differences of up to 1.63°C between the new and 5 year old screens.” (Tsinko, 2016)</p>
<p>Change of screen type: airflow issues</p>	<p>- Change to airflow through screen (e.g. changing the type of naturally vented screen or changing from an “unaspirated” to an</p>	<p>- “van der Meulen & Brandsma (2008) [Exp] looked at ten different aspirated and non-aspirated screens including Stevenson type and found that differences can add up to 1°C and mainly</p>

	<p>“aspirated” screen, etc.)</p>	<p>result from the differences in air circulation speed and the response time of various screens (van der Meulen & Brandsma, 2008).” (Tsinko, 2016)</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - “Naturally aspirated COOP sensors generally had warmer (+0.48°C) daily maximum and cooler (-0.36°C) minimum temperatures than USCRN, with considerable variability among stations.” (Leeper et al., 2015) [Obs] - “The field experiment was performed over a 1-year period to evaluate aspirated and non-aspirated Stevenson screen configurations used at the Meteorological Service of Canada’s Automated Weather Stations. The results show the non-aspirated screen is warmer than the aspirated screen duct location by 0.11°C on average with a significant increase in the maximum daily temperature of 0.22°C due to radiant heating effects. Temperature differences up to 2.1°C were observed between the aspirated and non-aspirated screens with a mean increase of 0.46°C following 30-min periods of mean global radiation greater than 200 W/m² and mean wind speed less than 2 m/s.” (Hoover & Yao, 2018) [Exp]
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Table 3: Examples of quantified effect of changes to observation methodology or procedures on surface air temperature

<p>Type of change to observation methodology or procedure</p>	<p>Proposed mechanisms by which change affects surface air temp.</p>	<p>Examples of quantified effect of change on surface air temp.</p> <p>Exp = Experimental study Obs = Observational study</p>
<p>Change of observation time</p>	<p>- Poor timing of the 24-hour period over which maximum or minimum daily temperature is measured can introduce</p>	<p>- “The bias resulted from a nation-wide change in observing procedure at principal stations in 1961. [...] Annually, magnitudes [of the bias] were typically from 0.6 to 0.8°C in the east and much</p>

	bias into the temperature record due to measuring the same (or similar) maximum or minimum across two measurement “days” (24-hour periods).	smaller at 0.2°C in the west.” (Vincent & Gullet, 1999) [Obs] - “We have shown that the TOB [time observation bias] in the United States can be quite large - as much as 2°C - and that the difference in biases, e.g., when the observation time changes from the late afternoon to near sunrise, is even greater. ” (Karl et al., 1986)
Change of algorithm for calculation of mean temperature	- Changing how daily “mean” temperature is calculated (e.g. average of daily max and min vs. average of several hourly measurements, etc.) can introduce a shift into a temperature record.	- “The algorithm used for the calculation of mean temperature will have an effect on longterm temperature measurements if there is a change from one algorithm to another [...] Victoria et al. ⁵³ noted a shift of -0.18°C arising from a 1938 change in algorithm in Brazil. There have been a number of studies ^{50,51,54-56} which have assessed systematic differences between two or more of the [mean calculation] methods described above. In general, these have found that differences tend to vary according to the nature of the location (...) and the season, but that differences between methods of 0.1-0.2°C on a network-wide basis, and 0.5-1.0°C at the most extreme individual sites , are typical.” (Trewin, 2010)

Section 3: Conclusion

There are thus many known physical causes of artifacts affecting surface air temperature measurements that can disrupt or bias a temperature record. Some of these artifacts can correspond to permanent shifts in mean annual temperature that can have magnitudes of the order of 1°C.

One can imagine possible changes to observation, measurement, or other procedures at the weather stations or in their immediate vicinities that could have produced the shift occurring at around 1998 in Eastern Canada stations. Examples include:

- deciding to base official temperature records on measurements from automatic weather stations rather than manual stations as of a certain date (even if the automatic stations were functional for some time prior to the switch-over date);

- upgrading or changing the type of temperature screen over the course of a year at many stations, e.g., by: implementing mechanical aspiration on all screens; refurbishing screen surfaces; replacing screens with a screen-type having inadequate back-radiation shielding; or other changes to screens;
- changing thermometer types, including associated electronics or other equipment;
- changing snow management practices or methods at airports introducing a local change of albedo;
- changing procedures at weather stations following an extreme weather event (e.g. the Ice Storm of 1998) to mitigate future damage, power outages, or other problems (an extreme weather event such as the 1998 Ice Storm could also affect the land use / land cover characteristics in the vicinity of the weather station and/or the instruments themselves);

and so on.

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After this, researcher Lucie A. Vincent responded as follows.

3.2.3 Final response of Environment Canada researcher Lucie A. Vincent regarding the 1998 step-increase feature

Lucie Vincent responded to my July 5, 2021 email on August 13, 2021 (page 000009 of Appendix F.2 of this report), as follows:

From: Vincent, Lucie (ECCC) <Lucie.Vincent@ec.gc.ca>
Sent: August 13, 2021 12:18 PM
To: Joseph Hickey
Cc: Hartwell, Megan (ECCC); Wang, Xiaolan (ECCC); Carou, Silvina (ECCC); Tatjana Dahlhaus
Subject: {External} RE: Bank of Canada's use of the 3rd Gen. AHCCD
Attachments: Vincent_and_coauthors_Third_Gen_Homog_Temp_AO_Jun2020.pdf

Hi Joseph,

Sorry for the late response.

Over the past years, we have carefully conducted an in-depth homogeneity assessment of the temperature records in Canada and we have adjusted the data when necessary (please see the attached paper). The data are now published at the following site:

<https://www.canada.ca/en/environment-climate-change/services/climate-change/science-research-data/climate-trends-variability/adjusted-homogenized-canadian-data.html>

We have not detected a positive shift around 1998 in the annual mean temperature of the selected stations due to automation or to any other non-climatic causes. This shift identified visually when the time series is focused on the 1960-2020 period is probably due to climate variability only. Our results regarding temperature homogenization and trends are in agreement with the findings of other regions around the globe.

Thank you for your interest in our work.

Lucie

Lucie A. Vincent

Research Climatologist / Climatologue chercheur

Climate Research Division / Division de la recherche climatique

Science and Technology Branch / Direction générale de la science et technologie

Environment and Climate Change Canada / Environnement et Changement climatique Canada

4905 Dufferin Street / 4905 rue Dufferin

Toronto, Ontario, Canada, M3H 5T4

Telephone / Téléphone : 416-739-4337

Facsimile / Télécopieur : 416-739-5700

Email / Courriel: Lucie.Vincent@canada.ca

The 1998 step-increase feature in the annually-averaged temperature time-series for many Canadian stations was therefore left essentially unaddressed by Environment Canada, and remains in place in the AHCCD dataset to this day, including in the 4th generation of the data, as can be seen from the graphs in Appendix C of this report.

3.3 More than 10,000 instances for which the daily minimum temperature was greater than the daily maximum temperature in the 2nd generation AHCCD

On December 7, 2020, Bank of Canada Economist Julien McDonald-Guimond sent an email to Environment Canada researchers with an inquiry about the 2nd generation AHCCD daily temperature records, noting he had found some cases in which the daily minimum temperature (T_{min}^D) was greater than the daily maximum temperature (T_{max}^D) for the same day and for the same AHCCD station.

McDonald-Guimond's email of December 7, 2020 is as follows:

From: Julien McDonald-Guimond <JMcDonald-Guimond@bank-banque-canada.ca>
Sent: December 7, 2020 3:12 P.M.
To: DCCA / AHCCD (EC) <ec.dccah-ahccd.ec@canada.ca>
Subject: Inquiry on AHCCD daily data

Category/Catégorie: Non-Sensitive/Non-Délicat

Hi,

I wish to inquire about the AHCCD daily data. I've discovered that some entries appear to be inconsistent, with maximum temperatures being lower than minimum temperatures. For instance, see Yellowknife on 1971-03-03, Toronto on 2018-03-25, or Winnipeg on 1994-12-12.

Would you be able to provide some explanations and, if need be, possible solutions?

Thank you very much,

Julien

Julien McDonald-Guimond
Économiste | Economist
Section des études sur l'économie canadienne | Canadian Economic Studies Division
Analyse de l'économie canadienne | Canadian Economic Analysis
234 Wellington Street, Ottawa, ON K1A 0G9
Téléphone | Telephone : 613.782.7083
JMcDonald-Guimond@bank-banque-canada.ca

McDonald-Guimond sent a second email on December 9, 2020 with an attached table listing the instances of $T_{min}^D > T_{max}^D$ that he had found. McDonald-Guimond's December 9, 2020 email is included on page 000003 of Appendix F.2 of this report. The attachment to McDonald-

Guimond's December 9, 2020 email, which Environment Canada's Access to Information office initially failed to include in its release (see the correspondence in Appendix F.3), was eventually provided and is included as Appendix F.4 of this report.

McDonald-Guimond's table contains 10,159 instances of daily temperature records with $T_{min}^D > T_{max}^D$. Affected records occurred in all Canadian provinces and territories.

A histogram of the differences $T_{min}^D - T_{max}^D$ for the 10,159 instances shown in McDonald-Guimond's table is shown in Figure 10.

Figure 10: Histogram of differences $T_{min}^D - T_{max}^D$ from the table of 10,159 instances of $T_{min}^D > T_{max}^D$ created by Bank of Canada Economist Julien McDonald-Guimond from the 2nd generation of the AHCCD.

For the 10,159 instances, the median difference between T_{min}^D and T_{max}^D was 0.80°C (vertical red line in Figure 10), the average difference was 1.21°C, and the maximum difference, which was for Cape Dorset, Nunavut, on February 25, 1995, was 30°C.

Environment Canada Climate Data Analyst Megan Hartwell replied to McDonald-Guimond on January 13, 2021 (pages 000002-000003 of Appendix F.2 of this report), as follows:

De : DCAH / AHCCD (EC) <cec.dccah-ahccd.ec@canada.ca>
Envoyé : 13 janvier 2021 10:29

À : Julien McDonald-Guimond <JMcDonald-Guimond@bank-banque-canada.ca>; DCCA / AHCCD (EC) <ec.dccah-ahccd.ec@canada.ca>
Cc : Vincent, Lucie (EC) <lucie.vincent@canada.ca>
Objet : {External} RE: Inquiry on AHCCD daily data

Hello Julien,

I'd like to thank you for your patience as we sorted out this issue. We were quite surprised by the frequency of the issue you reported, and have taken some time to go through the data carefully.

The first thing I noticed when going through your data is you are using the second generation of homogenized temperature. I would like to bring your attention to the third generation of homogenized data, which includes additional stations and a focus on RCS and NavCan stations. In the future only this generation of data will be updated, so I recommend using it for your research.

To access the third generation, please use the AHCCD site at:
<https://www.canada.ca/en/environment-climate-change/services/climate-change/science-research-data/climate-trends-variability/adjusted-homogenized-canadian-data.html>

Unfortunately, the AHCCD site-page has not been updated yet and does not introduce the third generation; however, the documentation describes the third generation, and the data linked is that of the third generation.

You can also access the third generation at the FTP site below:
http://crd-data-donnees-rdc.ec.gc.ca/CDAS/products/AHCCD_daily/

The files related to the third generation do not have "Gen2" attached to their filenames.

When examining the issue of tmin being greater than tmax, we should consider that it is possible for this to occur in reality. The observing period differs for these two elements at some stations, where the minimum temperature in one window may actually be higher than the maximum temperature in another. That being said, most of the occurrences you noted occur when the minimum temperature has been adjusted for homogeneity. Typically the minimum temperature is raised to create a homogeneous record, and this has resulted in it sometimes coming close to, or crossing the maximum temperature. We have resolved this error by changing this adjusted temperature to maintain the "min" and "max" values respectively.

This correction was made on the 3rd generation data for data up to the end of 2019. However we are in the process of updating this dataset to show the 2020 data, which will also have this issue resolved. If you are okay waiting, I can notify you when the 2020 data is available.

Thanks again for pointing this out, it helps us to provide the best data possible. Please let me know if you find any other irregularities in the data set.

Megan Hartwell

Climate Data Analyst, Climate Research Division
Environment and Climate Change Canada / Government of Canada
megan.hartwell@canada.ca / Tel.: 416-739-4349

Analyste des données climatologiques, Recherche climatique
Environnement et Changement climatique Canada / Gouvernement du Canada
megan.hartwell@canada.ca / Tél.: 416-739-4349

According to Hartwell's January 13, 2021 email, Environment Canada researchers were "quite surprised by the frequency of the issue [McDonald-Guimond] reported".

In her email, Hartwell stated that: "most of the occurrences [McDonald-Guimond] noted occur when the minimum temperature has been adjusted for homogeneity. Typically the minimum temperature is raised to create a homogeneous record, and this has resulted in it sometimes coming close to, or crossing the maximum temperature. We have resolved this error by changing this adjusted temperature to maintain the 'min' and 'max' values respectively."

Hartwell followed up with a February 15, 2021 email to McDonald-Guimond (pages 000071-000072 of Appendix F.2 of this report), as follows:

De : Hartwell, Megan (EC) <megan.hartwell@canada.ca>

Envoyé : 15 février 2021 3:51

À : Julien McDonald-Guimond <JMcDonald-Guimond@bank-banque-canada.ca>

Objet : {External} AHCCD temperature update 3rd Gen

Hello Julien,

I'm happy to inform you that the third generation of homogenized temperature has now been updated to include 2020 data

(http://crd-data-donnees-rdc.ec.gc.ca/CDAS/products/AHCCD_daily/)

A few improvements were made to the previous version, one of which you highlighted for us.

The days where tmax and tmin were reversed were fixed. There are several steps to this. If the data begins with this issue (the official archive version has tx < tn), the values are either manually corrected (typically missing a negative sign or decimal place) so [sic] moved to the average of the two values, plus or minus 0.1. The values then undergo the adjustments described in the paper. After all these adjustments were made the values were then checked

for $t_x < t_n$. If problematic, the adjusted value was corrected to respect the t_{max} and t_{min} relationship.

A number of missing mean values were estimated when either t_{max} or t_{min} were available. These values were estimated when the opposing element was available, using the dates on either side of the missing day of the same element.

Thank you again for choosing this dataset to work with and please let me know if you require anything further.

Megan Hartwell

Climate Data Analyst, Climate Research Division
Environment and Climate Change Canada / Government of Canada
megan.hartwell@canada.ca / Tel.: 416-739-4349

Analyste des données climatologiques, Recherche climatique
Environnement et Changement climatique Canada / Gouvernement du Canada
megan.hartwell@canada.ca / Tél.: 416-739-4349

In her February 15, 2021 email, Hartwell noted that, in the creation of the 3rd generation AHCCD, a check was made prior to homogenization to catch cases in which the daily minimum temperature was greater than the daily maximum temperature, which could occur, for example, due to a missing decimal point or a missing negative sign. Such a data-quality check procedure was also noted in Environment Canada researchers' paper presenting the 3rd generation AHCCD (Vincent et al. 2020, 176–77), in which it was stated that “Of the 780 homogenized data series of t_{max} and t_{min} throughout their complete period of record, only 0.0108% of data (about 2500 values) were identified as suspicious”, where a “suspicious” data-point includes a daily minimum temperature that is greater than the daily maximum temperature, among other possible problems, such as a daily maximum or minimum equal to 0°C on five consecutive days (Vincent et al. 2020, 177).

Since about 2500 “suspicious” values were found in the pre-homogenization data-quality check for the 3rd generation AHCCD, and since the 2nd generation AHCCD included fewer stations than the 3rd generation AHCCD, this means that at least approximately 7500 of the 10,159 instances with daily minimum temperatures greater than daily maximum temperatures identified by McDonald-Guimond resulted from the homogenization procedure, which, as Hartwell noted in her January 13, 2021 email, often involves raising the daily minimum temperature series, such that the daily minimum temperature sometimes becomes higher than the daily maximum temperature.

In Hartwell's February 15, 2021 email, she stated: "After all [the pre-homogenization data-quality check] adjustments were made the values were then checked for $t_x < t_n$. If problematic, the adjusted value was corrected to respect the t_{max} and t_{min} relationship." This means that Environment Canada made additional adjustments to the already-adjusted (homogenized) data in cases where the daily minimum temperature was greater than the daily maximum temperature, but it is unclear how the said additional adjustments were made.

4 Discussion

The presence of non-climatic artifacts in multi-decade temperature records, whether recognized and adjusted for or not, is a central problem in long-term temperature trend analysis, as many climatologists have readily acknowledged (Peterson et al. 1998; Vincent and Gullett 1999; Runnalls and Oke 2006; Pielke Sr., Davey, et al. 2007; Pielke Sr., Nielsen-Gammon, et al. 2007; Trewin 2010; Whitfield 2014; Vincent et al. 2009; 2012; 2020; Wan et al. 2025). However, while governmental departments responsible for producing publicly-available long-term temperature records apply procedures to adjust and homogenize the records in an attempt to remove certain artifacts and biases, there is potential for these agencies to be selective in their choices of which apparent artifacts to address, especially given the political context regarding so-called "climate change" and "global warming".

This report demonstrates Environment Canada's dismissive response to being alerted to a large, apparently non-climatic artifact in its flagship temperature time-series product, an artifact which could, on its own, be responsible for essentially all of the calculated warming for many Canadian locations over the past six or seven decades.

The said apparent artifact, referred to as the "1998 step-increase feature" in this report, is a stepwise increase of approximately 1°C in magnitude occurring at 1998 in the annual mean time-series of daily maximum, minimum, and mean temperatures for many stations across Canada in Environment Canada's Adjusted and Homogenized Canadian Climate Data (AHCCD).

Any such large and discontinuous stepwise shift in a temperature record is always considered to be of non-climatic origin in the scientific literature and in need of adjustment if it is to be used in trend analysis for a time period covering the affected portion of the data (see the references quoted in section 3.2.2).

Figure 2 of this report shows the 1998 step-increase feature for a selection of Eastern and Central Canadian AHCCD stations, and the figures in section 3.1.3 show that the 1998 step-increase feature is geographically widespread across Canada and that there are no other similar large and geographically widespread discontinuities in the AHCCD dataset at other years.

4.1 Environment Canada’s refusal to investigate or explain the 1998 step-increase feature

While working on a project involving the AHCCD in my then position as a data scientist for the Bank of Canada in 2021, I emailed the Environment Canada researchers responsible for the AHCCD twice, alerting them to the presence of the 1998 step-increase feature and asking for clarification about its origin.

Senior Environment Canada researcher Lucie A. Vincent, who has been centrally involved in the AHCCD’s development since its inception in the early 1990s to present (Gullett et al. 1992; Vincent and Gullett 1999; Vincent et al. 2009; 2012; 2020; Wan et al. 2025) responded to my emails.

In my first email, sent on July 24, 2021, I noted that an approximately 1°C stepwise increase in the annual mean temperature record for a station with essentially zero-slope segments in the data for 1960-1997 and 1998-2020 (as is the case for many AHCCD stations, as shown in Figure 2 and Appendix A of this report) would, on its own, produce an approximately 1.4°C increase in temperature over the period 1960-2020, therefore accounting for essentially all of the warming over that period claimed for many Canadian locations by other authors using the AHCCD temperature records (Vincent et al. 2020; Amano et al. 2021).

I also asked whether the apparent artifact could be related to the switch from manual to automatic measurement of temperature, which occurred for many AHCCD stations during the 1990s.

In her response to my first email, dated June 25, 2021, Vincent stated that the 1998 step-increase feature was not due to automation, writing that she “quickly checked the metadata for some of the stations and [she] was not able to retrieve a date of change from manual to automated observations around 1998”. Vincent also affirmed that the “[t]he results of our studies regarding the temperature homogenization and trends are in agreement with the findings of other regions from around the globe.”

In my second email to Lucie A. Vincent and her colleagues at Environment Canada, sent on July 5, 2021, I repeated my request for clarification about the origin of the 1998 step-increase feature, writing “I understand that, in your quick check of the metadata for several stations, you did not retrieve a date of change from manual to automated observations in 1998. However, I would like to determine the cause of the discontinuity, whatever the cause may be.” I noted that abrupt discontinuities in annual mean temperature records are always considered to be non-climatic in the scientific literature, and that there are many non-climatic biasing factors that could cause a shift of magnitude approximately 1°C. I listed many such factors, along with

scientific studies that have quantified their effects on surface air temperature, in three tables in the appendix to my email.

Notably, among the references I cited in my second email, was a quote from Vincent herself stating the following in an article published in 1999, regarding Environment Canada's protocol for adjusting temperature time-series to remove stepwise increases or decreases in the data (Vincent and Gullett 1999):

“steps greater than 0.6°C, identified in the annual series, are always adjusted regardless of the presence or lack of supporting station history”

Therefore, based on Environment Canada's own step-correction protocol as expressed in (Vincent and Gullett 1999), the stepwise increases of approximately 1°C in magnitude occurring at 1998 in the annual mean temperature time-series of many Canadian stations (Figure 2, Figure 5, Figure 7) should be assumed to be of artificial, non-climatic origin.

Lucie A. Vincent issued her final response to my inquiries on August 13, 2021, in-effect dismissing my concerns about the apparent non-climatic artifact (the 1998 step-increase feature). Vincent expressed no intention to investigate the 1998 step-increase feature to ascertain its origins, claimed it was “probably due to climate variability only”, apparently without having done more than a superficial “quick check” of metadata for some stations, and emphasized that “[o]ur results regarding temperature homogenization and trends are in agreement with the findings of other regions around the globe”, which does not address or resolve the specific discontinuity (the 1998 step-increase feature) in question.

4.2 Environment Canada's failure to “detect” the 1998 step-increase feature

In this section I show that Environment Canada's failure to recognize the 1998 artifact is due to the step detection procedure that it uncritically adopted.

In her final email response to my inquiries, Lucie A. Vincent wrote: “[w]e have not detected a positive shift around 1998 in the annual mean temperature of the selected stations due to automation or to any other non-climatic causes” (email of August 13, 2021, see section 3.2.3 and page 000009 of Appendix F.2).

The failure of Environment Canada researchers to “detect” the large (approximately 1°C) stepwise increase in the annual mean temperatures for many AHCCD stations appears to be attributable to the fact that the records for multiple pairs of nearby AHCCD stations all have the same step-increase feature. This is because Environment Canada's step-detection procedure relies on comparing the temperature record for an AHCCD station of interest (“test series”) with the temperature records of nearby AHCCD stations (“neighbouring series”) in order to expose

large values in the differences in annual mean temperatures for pairs of tested and neighbouring series.

Figures in the 2020 paper co-authored by Lucie A. Vincent presenting the 3rd generation of the AHCCD and explaining the methods and procedures used to create it (Vincent et al. 2020) demonstrate how the presence of the same stepwise discontinuity in pairs of neighbouring AHCCD stations can result in the step not being flagged at either station.

Vincent and co-authors' homogenization procedure is based on the presumption that an artifact will be located at a single station and that real climatic changes will affect neighboring stations. The presumption is falsified if many stations are externally affected or changed in the same year, such as with equipment modernization, scheduled site upkeep, or national or regional changes in monitoring protocols, for example. In any case, any large sudden year-to-year step should be assumed to be an artifact needing investigation and correction.

Figure 11 of this report is a copy of Figure 9 of Vincent et al. (2020). This figure belongs to a subsection of the "Data and methods" section of Vincent et al. (2020) entitled "*Example of Detecting Shifts Using Neighbour's Observations as Reference Series*". The authors use the AHCCD temperature record for Moncton, New Brunswick as an example to demonstrate how their step-detection method works. The authors compare the annual mean of daily maximum temperatures (Tmax) and the annual mean of daily minimum temperatures (Tmin) for Moncton with those for Fredericton, New Brunswick, which is located 180km from Moncton and which is taken to be a neighbouring series for the purposes of the authors' step-detection procedure.

Notably, as can be seen from Figure 2a and Figure 2b of this report, the AHCCD records for Moncton and Fredericton show two of the clearest examples of the 1998 step-increase feature that is the main focus of this report.

In applying their step-detection procedure, Vincent et al. (2020) subtracted the annual mean temperature series Tmax for Fredericton from the annual mean series Tmax for Moncton, producing a time-series representing the difference in Tmax across the two records. This is shown in Figure 11a (Figure 9a of Vincent et al. (2020)). The same differencing was done for Tmin for the two AHCCD stations, shown in Figure 11b (Figure 9b of Vincent et al. (2020)).

In both Figure 11a and Figure 11b of this report, no stepwise shift or other large increase or decrease in the difference series is observed around 1998. The 1998 step-increase feature does not appear in Figure 11a or Figure 11b because it is present in Tmax and Tmin for *both* Moncton and Fredericton, such that subtracting the annual mean series for one AHCCD station from that of the other causes the 1998 shift-increase feature to vanish.

The difference series in Figure 11a and Figure 11b are what are used to detect steps in Vincent et al. (2020)'s procedure. Indeed, the authors detected steps in the series for Moncton at 1926 and 1940 (dashed vertical lines in Figure 11a and Figure 11b), and attributed them to relocation

of the measurement instruments in 1926, and to the authors' joining of the record from a downtown weather station with the record for the airport weather station at the joining year 1940.

Figures 11g and 11h show the resulting homogenized annual mean temperature series (Tmax and Tmin, respectively) for Moncton after Vincent and co-authors adjusted them for the detected shifts in 1926 and 1940 (solid red line in Figure 11g and solid blue line in Figure 11h). As can be seen from Figures 11g and 11h, the 1998 step-increase feature is retained in the AHCCD time-series for Moncton, following all of Vincent et al. (2020)'s step-detection and adjustment procedures.

Basically, when the same 1998 artifact occurred in compared neighboring stations then the researchers concluded that there was no artifact. More and yearly-synchronous artifacts became no artifacts needing correction and the 1998 steps were preserved in further analysis. The researchers make no mention that many more stations also have the 1998 feature, which in a sense extends so-called neighbouring to most of Canada.

Figure 11: Copy of Figure 9 of Vincent et al. (2020). The original caption reads as: "Differences in annual mean of (a) tmax and (b) tmin between the tested series (Moncton) and neighbour (Fredericton); (c) and (d) seasonal mean and (e) and (f) 12 quantile-bin mean differences (5-year-after-1940 minus 5-year-before-1940) in the daily Moncton-minus-Fredericton series; and (g) and (h) the annual mean series before (dotted line) and after (solid line) applying the adjustments. In (a), (b), (g), and (h), the vertical lines represent the dates of the detected shifts (1926 and 1940). In (e) and (f), the horizontal axis is percentile, and the dotted line represents the spline fitted to the 12 quantile-bins mean."

4.3 The 1998 step-increase feature accounts for essentially all calculated warming for all of Canada

As was shown in the maps in Figure 7 (red circles, with $S_r > 1$), a discernible stepwise increase in annual average temperature occurring at 1998 is present in the majority of AHCCD temperature records across Canada.

The widespread presence of the 1998 step-increase feature for individual AHCCD records across Canada causes a stepwise increase to also be apparent at the year 1998 in Environment Canada researchers Vincent et al.'s (2020) time-series of temperature anomalies for all of Canada, which they obtain from gridding the individual AHCCD records. This is shown in Figure 12, below, which is a copy of Figure 12 from Vincent et al. (2020). The stepwise increase at 1998 is apparent in their final data without needing any step detection analysis.

(a) trends annual tmean 1948-2018

(b) annual tmean anomalies

Figure 12: Copy of Figure 12 of Vincent et al. (2020). The original caption reads as “Trends in (a) annual mean of tmean for 1948–2018 ($^{\circ}\text{C}$ per 71 yr). Grid squares with trends statistically significant at the 5% level are marked with a dot. (b) Annual mean of tmean anomalies for Canada, 1948–2018. The red line indicates the anomalies before adjustment, and the black line is an 11 yr running mean.”

Vincent et al. (2020) use the time-series in Figure 12b to calculate a warming of 1.74°C for all of Canada over the time period 1948-2018. However, in Figure 12b the segments of the all-Canada temperature anomaly time-series (Figure 12b) for 1948-1997 and for 1998-2018 are each essentially flat, with essentially zero slope. If the artificial stepwise increase at 1998 in Figure 12b was removed, then the entire time-series from 1948-2018 would have essentially zero slope. The bulk of the claimed 1.74°C warming trend for all of Canada from 1948-2018 is due to the artificial stepwise increase of approximately 1°C in magnitude occurring at 1998. This point is further demonstrated below.

To make the argument in this section more concrete, I have digitized the Figure 12b of Vincent et al. (2020), using WebPlotDigitizer (Rohatgi 2025) to obtain a reproduction of the data points, and plotted the digitized time-series in the left panel of Figure 13.

Figure 13: Left panel: Annual Tmean anomalies from Figure 12b of Vincent et al. (2020). Red line: linear least squares fit producing a trend (slope times 71 years) of 1.92°C; green line: trend of 1.74°C calculated using the method of Sen (1968); solid magenta line: average of the data points for 1948-1997; dashed magenta line: average of the data points for 1997-2018. Right panel: The annual Tmean anomalies from the left panel, with the data-points for 1998-2018 lowered by an amount equal to the difference in the averages for 1998-2018 and 1948-1997. Red line: linear least squares fit producing a trend of 0.3°C for 1948-2018; green line: trend of 0.29°C for 1948-2018 calculated using the method of Sen (1968).

The red line in the left panel of Figure 13 shows a linear least-squares fit with an increasing trend (slope times 71 years) of 1.92°C. Applying the slope estimation method of Sen (1968), which is the method used by Environment Canada researchers in Vincent et al. (2020), produces a trend of 1.74°C, which is the same value as that reported by Vincent et al. (2020). The green line shows the fit obtained from the Sen (1968) method. The solid magenta horizontal line in Figure 13 shows the average of the annual Tmean anomalies for 1948-1997, and the dashed magenta horizontal line shows the average of the annual Tmean anomalies for 1998-2018.

In the right panel of Figure 13, I have removed the stepwise increase beginning at 1998 in the annual Tmean anomaly time-series by lowering the values of the data-points for 1998-2018 by an amount equal to the difference in the averages of the data-points for the segments 1998-2018 and 1948-1997 (i.e., the data-points for 1998-2018 were each lowered by an amount equal to the difference in the values of the solid and dashed magenta lines in the left panel of Figure 13).

The red line in the right panel of Figure 13 shows a linear least squares fit with an increasing trend of 0.3°C, and the green shows the fit line obtained from the method of Sen (1968), which produces an increasing trend of 0.29°C. To test for statistical significance of trends obtained from Sen's slope estimation method, Vincent et al. (2020) use the Zhang et al. (2000) implementation of the non-parametric Kendall's tau test (Kendall 1955), which can be applied using the "zyp" software package for R (Bronaugh et al. 2023). Applying this method to the adjusted data in the right panel of Figure 13b produces a *p*-value of 0.29, meaning that the trend for the adjusted data is not statistically significant. That is, the null hypothesis of zero slope is not rejected at any conventional significance level.

4.4 Homogenization can create new artifacts, such as $T_{min}^D > T_{max}^D$

Section 3.3 concerns a separate issue revealed in ATI email release. A Bank of Canada economist (Julien McDonald-Guimond) had identified 10,159 instances in the 2nd generation of the AHCCD for which the daily minimum temperature was greater than the daily maximum temperature, in data records that had been homogenized by increasing minimum temperatures.

In her email of January 13, 2021, Environment Canada Climate Data Analyst Megan Hartwell stated: "[m]ost of the occurrences [McDonald-Guimond] noted occur when the minimum temperature has been adjusted for homogeneity. Typically the minimum temperature is raised to create a homogeneous record, and this has resulted in it sometimes coming close to, or crossing the maximum temperature. We have resolved this error by changing this adjusted temperature to maintain the "min" and "max" values respectively."

Environment Canada's "resolution" to the issue of identified daily minimum temperatures being greater than daily maximum temperatures, in data that had already been adjusted by raising minimum temperatures, was to make further changes to the data. It is not clear from Hartwell's statement in her January 13, 2021 email, or from Hartwell's follow-up email of February 15, 2021, whether Environment Canada's "resolution" involved lowering affected minimum temperatures such that they would fall below the corresponding daily maxima, raising affected maximum temperatures such that they would rise above the corresponding daily minima, or some other type of adjustment.

It may also be relevant to the institutional context that Environment Canada's ATI office failed to provide McDonald-Guimond's table listing the 10,159 instances in its initial document release, and only provided it after a pointed follow-up request was made, as documented in Appendix F.3 of this report. There is no way of knowing the magnitude of the issue identified by McDonald-Guimond (at least 10,159 affected station-days) from the text of the released emails alone.

5 Conclusion

A significant non-climatic artifact exists in the AHCCD, which is a stepwise increase of 1°C in magnitude occurring at 1998 in the annual average temperature records for most AHCCD stations across Canada. These yearly stepwise anomalies in the temperature records cannot arise from any known natural phenomenon. The said artifact at 1998, on its own, can cause essentially all of the claimed multi-decadal (since 1948) warming (of approximately 1-2°C) calculated for Canada. My conclusion is based on the temperature data itself, and the institutional context is revealed through access to information (ATI) documents. The reported climate warming of Canada appears to be entirely from a temperature measurement artifact.

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Appendix A: Graphs showing approximate upper and lower plateau values in annual average temperatures for the Eastern and Central Canadian AHCCD stations listed in Table A of the main text

This appendix contains figures in the format of Figure 3 of the main text, for all sixteen Eastern and Central Canadian AHCCD records listed in Table A of the main text.

Figure 3 of the main text, which was for the Moncton AHCCD station only, is reproduced as the first row of three panels in the figure in this appendix.

Appendix B: Annual average temperature series for the Western Canadian AHCCD stations listed in Table B of the main text

The figure in this appendix shows the annual averages of daily mean (T_{mean}), maximum (T_{max}), and minimum (T_{min}) temperatures, for the eight Western Canadian AHCCD stations listed in Table B of the main text.

Appendix C: Comparison of 3rd and 4th generation homogenized Canadian temperature data

C.1 Comparison of annual average temperature time-series from 3rd and 4th generation AHCCD, for the sixteen Eastern and Central Canadian AHCCD stations listed in Table A of the main text

The figure in this appendix sub-section shows annually-averaged temperature time-series for the sixteen Eastern and Central Canadian AHCCD stations listed in Table A of the main text, using the data from the 3rd generation AHCCD (blue, same data as shown in Figure 2 of the main text) and from the 4th generation AHCCD (orange).

C.2 Distributions of step sizes (Δ_S) and step size ratios (S_r) for the 4th generation AHCCD

The figures in this appendix sub-section, which are in the format of Figures 4 and 6 of the main text, show Δ_S and S_r as functions of break year, for window size $N=5$ years and $T=T_{\text{mean}}$, for the 4th generation AHCCD stations with sufficient data (650 stations for most break years).

C.3 Maps of Δ_S and S_r for the break year 1998 for the 4th generation AHCCD

The figures in this appendix sub-section, which are in the format of Figures 5 and 7 of the main text, show maps of Δ_S and S_r (defined in section 3.1.3 of the main text) for the break year 1998, with windows size $N=5$ years and $T=T_{\text{mean}}$, for the 4th generation AHCCD stations with sufficient data (650 stations).

T_{mean}
 Δ_S for $w_1 = 1993-1997$ and $w_2 = 1998-2002$
(650 stations with sufficient data)
(4th Generation AHCCD)

Tmean
 S_r for $w_1 = 1993-1997$ and $w_2 = 1998-2002$
(650 stations with sufficient data)
(4th Generation AHCCD)

Appendix D: Distributions of step sizes (Δ_s) and step size ratios (S_r) for different choices of T and N

This appendix contains figures showing Δ_s and S_r (defined in section 3.1.3 of the main text), for different values of the window size N and for the three different types of temperature records (Tmean, Tmax, and Tmin).

All figures in this appendix, use all 3rd generation AHCCD records with at least 350 days of daily data for all years belonging to the windows w_1 and w_2 (see section 3.1.3 of the main text for definitions).

Tmean
(Two 2-year windows; "break year" is first year of later window)

Tmax
(Two 2-year windows; "break year" is first year of later window)

Tmin
(Two 2-year windows; "break year" is first year of later window)

Tmean
(Two 5-year windows; "break year" is first year of later window)

Tmax
(Two 5-year windows; "break year" is first year of later window)

Tmin
(Two 5-year windows; "break year" is first year of later window)

Tmean
(Two 10-year windows; "break year" is first year of later window)

Tmax
(Two 10-year windows; "break year" is first year of later window)

Tmin
(Two 10-year windows; "break year" is first year of later window)

Tmean
(Two 2-year windows; "break year" is first year of later window)

Tmax
(Two 2-year windows; "break year" is first year of later window)

Tmin
(Two 2-year windows; "break year" is first year of later window)

Tmean
(Two 5-year windows; "break year" is first year of later window)

Tmax
(Two 5-year windows; "break year" is first year of later window)

Tmin
(Two 5-year windows; "break year" is first year of later window)

Tmean
(Two 10-year windows; "break year" is first year of later window)

Tmax
(Two 10-year windows; "break year" is first year of later window)

Tmin
(Two 10-year windows; "break year" is first year of later window)

Appendix E: Maps showing trend signs and significance for pre-step periods 1977-1997 and 1960-1997

This appendix contains graphs in the format of Figures 8 and 9 of the main text (section 3.1.4), for the two time periods 1977-1997 and 1960-1997.

As for Figures 8 and 9 of the main text, the figures in this appendix use 3rd generation AHCCD stations with at least 350 days of non-missing daily data for all years in the relevant time-period.

Trend in Tmean for period 1977-1997 (linear least squares fit)

Trend in Tmean for period 1977-1997 (method of Sen/Zhang, sig. level $\alpha = 0.05$)

Trend in Tmean for period 1960-1997 (linear least squares fit)

Trend in Tmean for period 1960-1997 (method of Sen/Zhang, sig. level $\alpha = 0.05$)

Appendix F: Emails obtained by Access to Information request from Environment Canada

F.1 Environment Canada's Response Letter for the Access to Information request

Below is a copy of Environment Canada's Response Letter for the Access to Information request, which contains a copy of the text of the request.

Fontaine Building
200 Sacré Coeur Blvd, 13th Floor
Gatineau, Québec K1A 0H3

Your File Votre référence

Communications ECCC &
Bank of Canada

Our File Notre référence

A-2022-00711 / MM2

March 21, 2023

Mr. Joseph Hickey

Dear Mr. Hickey,

We have completed processing your request under the *Access to Information Act* (the Act) for:

"I request the emails sent or received by at least one of {Lucie Vincent}, {Silvina Carou}, {Xiaolan Wang}, and {Megan Hartwell}, and sent or received by at least one employee of the Bank of Canada, and the attachments to the respondent emails.

In other words, these are emails between one or more Environment Canada scientists {Lucie Vincent, Silvina Carou, Xiaolan Wang, Megan Hartwell} and one or more Bank of Canada employees (at any level), and the attachments. The respondent period is January 1, 2020 to present."

Attached please find the complete release package in response to this request. Please be advised that some information has been withheld in accordance with subsection 19(1) of the Act. A copy of the relevant section is attached.

Please be advised that you are entitled to file a complaint with the Information Commissioner concerning the processing of your request within sixty days of the receipt of this notice. In the event you decide to avail yourself of this right, your notice of complaint should be addressed to:

Information Commissioner of Canada
30 Victoria Street
Gatineau, Québec K1A 1H3

If you have any questions regarding this request, please do not hesitate to contact Martine Mainville by email at martine.mainville@ec.gc.ca.

Yours sincerely,

Emmerson, Shelley

Shelley Emmerson
Director, Access to Information and Privacy

Digitally signed by: Emmerson, Shelley
DN: CN = Emmerson, Shelley C = CA O = GC OU = EC-EC
Date: 2023.03.21 14:59:30 -04'00'

Enclosures

F.2 Emails released by Environment Canada

Below is the package of documents (101 pages) released by Environment Canada pursuant to the Access to Information request.

Hartwell, Megan (ECCC)

From: DCCAHA / AHCCD (EC) <ec.dccah-ahccd.ec@canada.ca>
Sent: January 14, 2021 9:46 AM
To: Julien McDonald-Guimond; DCCAHA / AHCCD (EC)
Cc: Vincent, Lucie (EC)
Subject: RE: Inquiry on AHCCD daily data

Hi Julien,

Thank you for your understanding. The third generation was released in August 2020. The version on the website does not have the tmin>tmax corrected but the updated version, including the 2020 data will. This data should be available in February, and I am happy to inform you when it is posted.

The AHCCD website, unfortunately, does not point directly to the daily data, you are correct. However you should be able to find it using google, through the Open Canada website. When I search "AHCCD daily" it is the first link: [Adjusted and Homogenized Canadian Climate Data – Daily Temperature and Precipitation AHCCD – daily T&P - Open Government Portal \(canada.ca\)](#)

Thanks,
Megan

From: Julien McDonald-Guimond <JMcDonald-Guimond@bank-banque-canada.ca>
Sent: January 14, 2021 9:25 AM
To: DCCAHA / AHCCD (EC) <ec.dccah-ahccd.ec@canada.ca>
Cc: Vincent, Lucie (EC) <lucie.vincent@canada.ca>
Subject: RE: Inquiry on AHCCD daily data

Category/Catégorie: Non-Sensitive/Non-Délicat

Hi Megan,

No problem at all. I understand that making these kinds of verifications can take a lot of time. I'm grateful for your thorough answer, it clarifies things greatly. I understand that the 3rd generation was published over the summer, and if so I definitely missed it. I will retrieve them now but just to be certain, is the correction that you mentioned currently in the files on the FTP site, or will you be uploading the correction only once the 2020 vintage is ready? And regarding this new vintage, do you have an approximate month of release?

With respect to the AHCCD website, I have never been able to locate the daily frequency data from there. I actually needed some guidance from someone in your team last year to get that FTP link. Can the daily data be accessed from the AHCCD website or else how could someone easily find them?

Thank you very much,
Julien

Julien Mc Donald-Guimond

Économiste | Economist

Section des études sur l'économie canadienne | Canadian Economic Studies Division

Analyse de l'économie canadienne | Canadian Economic Analysis

234 rue Wellington Street, Ottawa ON K1A 0G9

Téléphone | Telephone : 613.782.7083

JMcDonald-Guimond@bank-banque-canada.ca

De : DCCA / AHCCD (EC) <ec.dccah-ahccd.ec@canada.ca>

Envoyé : 13 janvier 2021 10:29

À : Julien McDonald-Guimond <JMcDonald-Guimond@bank-banque-canada.ca>; DCCA / AHCCD (EC) <ec.dccah-ahccd.ec@canada.ca>

Cc : Vincent, Lucie (EC) <lucie.vincent@canada.ca>

Objet : {External} RE: Inquiry on AHCCD daily data

Hello Julien,

I'd like to thank you for your patience as we sorted out this issue. We were quite surprised by the frequency of the issue you reported, and have taken some time to go through the data carefully.

The first thing I noticed when going through your data is you are using the second generation of homogenized temperature. I would like to bring your attention to the third generation of homogenized data, which includes additional stations and a focus on RCS and NavCanada stations. In the future only this generation of data will be updated, so I recommend using it for your research.

To access the third generation, please use the AHCCD site at:

<https://www.canada.ca/en/environment-climate-change/services/climate-change/science-research-data/climate-trends-variability/adjusted-homogenized-canadian-data.html>

Unfortunately that the AHCCD site-page has not been updated yet and does not introduce the third generation; however, the documentation describes the third generation, and the data linked is that of the third generation.

You can also access the third generation at the FTP site below:

http://crd-data-donnees-rdc.ec.gc.ca/CDAS/products/AHCCD_daily/

The files related to the third generation do not have "Gen2" attached to their filenames.

When examining the issue of tmin being greater than tmax, we should consider that it is possible for this to occur in reality. The observing period differs for these two elements at some stations, where the minimum temperature in one window may actually be higher than the maximum temperature in another. That being said, most of the occurrences you noted occur when the minimum or maximum temperature has been adjusted for homogeneity. Typically the minimum temperature is raised to create a homogeneous record, and this has resulted in it sometimes coming close to, or crossing the maximum temperature. We have resolved this error by changing this adjusted temperature to maintain the "min" and "max" values respectively.

This correction was made on the 3rd generation data for data up to the end of 2019. However we are in the process of updating this dataset to show the 2020 data, which will also have this issue resolved. If you are okay waiting, I can notify you when the 2020 data is available.

Thanks again for pointing this out, it helps us to provide the best data possible. Please let me know if you find any other irregularities in the data set.

Megan Hartwell

Climate Data Analyst, Climate Research Division
Environment and Climate Change Canada / Government of Canada
megan.hartwell@canada.ca / Tel.: 416-739-4349

Analyste de données climatologiques, Recherche climatique
Environnement et Changement climatique Canada / Gouvernement du Canada
megan.hartwell@canada.ca / Tél.: 416-739-4349

From: Julien McDonald-Guimond <JMcDonald-Guimond@bank-banque-canada.ca>
Sent: December 9, 2020 5:46 PM
To: DCCAH / AHCCD (EC) <ec.dccah-ahccd.ec@canada.ca>
Cc: Vincent, Lucie (EC) <lucie.vincent@canada.ca>
Subject: RE: Inquiry on AHCCD daily data

Category/Catégorie: Non-Sensitive/Non-Délicat

Hi Megan,

Thank you very much for your help. You can find attached a table with all instances of Tmin > Tmax that I've found in the AHCCD daily data.

All the best,
Julien

De : DCCAH / AHCCD (EC) <ec.dccah-ahccd.ec@canada.ca>
Envoyé : 9 décembre 2020 11:37
À : Julien McDonald-Guimond <JMcDonald-Guimond@bank-banque-canada.ca>; DCCAH / AHCCD (EC) <ec.dccah-ahccd.ec@canada.ca>
Cc : Vincent, Lucie (EC) <lucie.vincent@canada.ca>
Objet : {External} RE: Inquiry on AHCCD daily data

Hi Julien,

Thank you for your inquiry. I agree that there seem to be some inconsistencies in the stations you noted below, however I need some more time to understand why these things occurred and how to best fix them.

I will begin working on this now, and follow up with you when I have some results to share. If you find any further occurrences in the mean time, please do not hesitate to reach out to me.

Megan Hartwell

Climate Data Analyst, Climate Research Division
Environment and Climate Change Canada / Government of Canada

megan.hartwell@canada.ca / Tel.: 416-739-4349

Analyste de données climatologiques, Recherche climatique
Environnement et Changement climatique Canada / Gouvernement du Canada
megan.hartwell@canada.ca / Tél.: 416-739-4349

From: Julien McDonald-Guimond <JMcDonald-Guimond@bank-banque-canada.ca>

Sent: December 7, 2020 3:12 PM

To: DCCAH / AHCCD (EC) <ec.dccah-ahccd.ec@canada.ca>

Subject: Inquiry on AHCCD daily data

Category/Catégorie: Non-Sensitive/Non-Délicat

Hi,

I wish to inquire about the AHCCD daily data. I've discovered that some entries appear to be inconsistent, with maximum temperatures being lower than minimal temperatures. For instance, see Yellowknife on 1971-03-03, Toronto on 2018-03-25, or Winnipeg on 1994-12-12.

Would you be able to provide me with some explanations and, if need be, possible solutions?

Thank you very much,

Julien

Julien Mc Donald-Guimond

Économiste | Economist

Section des études sur l'économie canadienne | Canadian Economic Studies Division

Analyse de l'économie canadienne | Canadian Economic Analysis

234 rue Wellington Street, Ottawa ON K1A 0G9

Téléphone | Telephone : 613.782.7083

JMcDonald-Guimond@bank-banque-canada.ca

1-year avg. of AHCCD daily temperatures

Hartwell,Megan (ECCC)

From: Vincent, Lucie (ECCC)
Sent: August 13, 2021 12:18 PM
To: Joseph Hickey
Cc: Hartwell, Megan (ECCC); Wang, Xiaolan (ECCC); Carou, Silvina (ECCC); Tatjana Dahlhaus
Subject: RE: Bank of Canada's use of the 3rd Gen. AHCCD
Attachments: Vincent_and_coauthors_Third_Gen_Homog_Temp_AO_Jun2020.pdf

Hi Joseph,

Sorry for the late response.

Over the past years, we have carefully conducted an in-depth homogeneity assessment of the temperature records in Canada and we have adjusted the data when necessary (please see the attached paper). The data are now published at the following site:

<https://www.canada.ca/en/environment-climate-change/services/climate-change/science-research-data/climate-trends-variability/adjusted-homogenized-canadian-data.html>

We have not detected a positive shift around 1998 in the annual mean temperature of the selected stations due to automation or to any other non-climatic causes. This shift identified visually when the time series is focused on the 1960-2020 period is probably due to climate variability only. Our results regarding temperature homogenization and trends are in agreement with the findings of other regions around the globe.

Thank you for your interest in our work.

Lucie

Lucie A. Vincent

Research Climatologist / Climatologue chercheur
Climate Research Division / Division de la recherche climatique
Science and Technology Branch / Direction générale de la science et technologie
Environment and Climate Change Canada / Environnement et Changement climatique Canada
4905 Dufferin Street / 4905 rue Dufferin
Toronto, Ontario, Canada, M3H 5T4
Telephone / Téléphone : 416-739-4337
Facsimile / Télécopieur : 416-739-5700
Email / Courriel: Lucie.Vincent@canada.ca

From: Joseph Hickey <JHickey@bank-banque-canada.ca>
Sent: July 19, 2021 8:11 AM
To: Vincent, Lucie (ECCC) <Lucie.Vincent@ec.gc.ca>
Cc: Hartwell, Megan (ECCC) <Megan.Hartwell@ec.gc.ca>; Wang, Xiaolan (ECCC) <Xiaolan.Wang@ec.gc.ca>; Carou, Silvina (ECCC) <Silvina.Carou@ec.gc.ca>; Tatjana Dahlhaus <tdahlhaus@bank-banque-canada.ca>
Subject: RE: Bank of Canada's use of the 3rd Gen. AHCCD

Category/Catégorie: Non-Sensitive/Non-Délicat

Dear Dr. Vincent,

Did you receive my email of July 5 (below)? Could you indicate a timeframe for your response? I continue to be interested in evaluating these artifacts.

Sincerely,
Joseph

From: Joseph Hickey
Sent: July 5, 2021 8:17 AM
To: 'Vincent, Lucie (EC)' <lucie.vincent@canada.ca>
Cc: Hartwell, Megan (EC) <megan.hartwell@canada.ca>; Wang, Xiaolan (EC) <xiaolan.wang@canada.ca>; Carou, Silvina (EC) <silvina.carou@canada.ca>; Tatjana Dahlhaus <tdahlhaus@bank-banque-canada.ca>
Subject: RE: Bank of Canada's use of the 3rd Gen. AHCCD

Category/Catégorie: Non-Sensitive/Non-Délicat

Dear Dr. Vincent,

Thank you for your email of June 25 responding to my inquiry about whether instrument automation could have caused a discontinuity occurring at around 1998 in the temperature records of many weather stations in Eastern Canada.

I understand that, in your quick check of the metadata for several stations, you did not retrieve a date of change from manual to automated observations around 1998. However, I would like to determine the cause of the discontinuity, whatever the cause might be.

In the appendix to this email (below), I argue that one must conclude that such a large abrupt shift can only be non-climatic. This is a well-established point, regarding yearly-averaged weather station temperature records. I've organized the appendix into sections as follows:

1. Large abrupt shifts in temperature records are always considered to be non-climatic
2. Examples of quantified effects of non-climatic changes on measured temperature
 - a. Table 1: Effect of land use / land cover (LULC) changes
 - b. Table 2: Effect of instrumentation changes
 - c. Table 3: Effect of changes to observation methodology or procedures
3. Conclusion
4. List of References

The appendix shows that there are several known physical causes of artifacts affecting surface air temperature measurements that can disrupt or bias a temperature record. Many such circumstances can produce permanent shifts in mean annual temperature that can have magnitudes of the order of 1°C.

We would, therefore, very much appreciate your help in confirming that the discontinuity at around 1998 is non-climatic and, if possible, in determining its likely actual cause.

Sincerely,

Joseph

--

Joseph Hickey, PhD

Data Scientist | Scientifique des données

Canadian Economic Analysis | Analyses de l'économie canadienne

Bank of Canada | Banque du Canada

234 rue Wellington Street, Ottawa ON K1A 0G9

Appendix

Section 1. Large abrupt shifts in temperature records are always considered to be non-climatic

Large abrupt shifts in temperature records are always considered to be non-climatic and must be investigated, and corrected for, if possible. The scientific literature has statements to this effect, such as the following.

Peterson et al. (1998), "Homogeneity adjustments of *in situ* atmospheric climate data: A review", *Int. J. Climatol.* 18:1493-1517

"Unfortunately, most long-term climatological time series have been affected by a number of non-climatic factors that make these data unrepresentative of the actual climate variation occurring over time. These factors include changes in: instruments, observing practices, station locations, formulae used to calculate means, and station environment (Jones et al., 1985; Karl and Williams, 1987; Gullett et al., 1990; Heino, 1994). **Some changes cause sharp discontinuities while other changes, particularly change in the environment around the station, can cause gradual biases in the data.** All of these inhomogeneities can bias a time series and lead to misinterpretations of the studied climate. It is important, therefore, to remove the inhomogeneities or at least determine the possible error they may cause."

Peterson & Easterling (1994), "Creation of homogeneous composite climatological reference series", *Int. J. Climatol.* 14:671-679

"Many of the research problems facing climatologists today, such as global climate change, require long homogeneous time series: time series where variations are caused only by variations of weather and climate (Conrad and Pollock, 1950). **However, it is rare to find long time series that do not have some artificial changes in their statistical characteristics.** Using data that have not been adjusted adequately for inhomogeneities can often lead to erroneous conclusions because the climate-change signal can be obscured easily or enhanced artificially by discontinuities in the data. For example, Hansen and Lebedeffs (1988) analysis of global surface-temperature trends indicates considerable warming in the 1980s around St Helena Island (16°S, 6°W). However, much of this 'warming' was actually due to an inhomogeneity in the St Helena Island time series caused by the station moving to a lower elevation (P. Michaels, pers. comm., 1992).

Inhomogeneities in time series arise either due to abrupt discontinuities or to effects that gradually increase over time. **Abrupt discontinuities occur as a result of instrument and exposure changes, station moves, and changes in calculation procedures for time-averaged values.** Inhomogeneities that occur as a gradually increasing effect generally develop as a result of a change in the environment surrounding a station, such as urbanization, or a gradual change in either the instrument calibration or the physical characteristics of the instrument apparatus (e.g. yellowing of a white plastic instrument shelter (Quale et al., 1991))."

Easterling & Peterson (1995), "A new method for detecting undocumented discontinuities in climatological time series", *Int. J. Climatol.* 15:369-377

"It is impossible to verify that a climatological time series is truly homogeneous, and it is very rare to find a long climatological time series that is even homogeneous relative to surrounding stations. Furthermore, even if there are accompanying metadata, in the form of station histories, that are used to make data adjustments for homogenization purposes, the potential still exists that some undocumented station change has affected the statistical characteristics of the time series. Station history files are often incomplete and may not routinely document changes that can cause a discontinuity. For example, Easterling and Peterson (1992) examined a

number of techniques for detecting discontinuities, and using data from the United States Historical Climatology Network (USHCN, Karl et al., 1990) demonstrated that discontinuities can be identified for such instances as replacing a thermometer with a new one of the same model, or simply calibrating the instrument.”

Jones et al. (1986), “Northern hemisphere surface air temperature variations: 1851-1984”, *J. Clim. App. Meteor.* 25:161-179

“It has long been known that the basic source of long term station air temperature records (WWR) contains many station records that are not homogeneous (i.e., they contain changes that result from nonclimatic factors). For example, values for individual months can be mispunched, misprinted or simply incorrect. More serious errors may arise from station moves, changes in observation times and the effects of environmental changes around the station. **These factors may cause spurious discontinuities and trends that are not the result of climatic change and which may obscure or distort any climate-related change.**”

Zurbenko et al. (1996), “Detecting discontinuities in time series of upper-air data: Development and demonstration of an adaptive filter technique”, *J. Climate* 9:3548-3560

[Here, referring to upper-air temperature data]

“**Unfortunately, these data contain systematic errors caused by changes in instruments, data acquisition procedures, etc. It is essential that systematic errors be identified and/or removed before these data can be used confidently in the context of greenhouse-gas-induced climate modification.**”

(...)

“The detection of abrupt changes due to instrumentation or data reduction procedures is complicated by the nature of daily temperature and humidity data. The time series of upper-air data can be characterized as high-frequency change combined with low-frequency seasonal and trend components. The seasonal components vary from year to year and, in the presence of the high-frequency component, are difficult to separate from abrupt discontinuities using parametric methods. **In addressing this problem we presume that changes in data due to instrument change are characterized by their abrupt and persistent nature. This behavior is contrasted with long-term climate or short-term weather systems.**”

The above passage emphasizes the *abrupt and persistent* nature of a non-climatic inhomogeneity, in contrast to long-term (decadal or longer) climate or short-term (minutes, hours, days) weather systems. This is relevant to the shift at around 1998 at Eastern Canada stations because it occurs between two regimes of twenty or more years with roughly zero trend, for many stations.

Lastly, in Vincent & Gullett (1999) shifts greater than 0.6 degrees Celsius were assumed to be non-climatic and therefore needing adjustment:

Vincent & Gullett (1999), “Canadian historical and homogeneous temperature datasets for climate change analysis”, *Int. J. Climatol.* 19:1375-1388

“The following rule was therefore implemented: **steps greater than 0.6°C, identified in the annual series, are always adjusted regardless of the presence or lack of supporting station history**; steps between 0.4 and 0.6°C are adjusted only with supporting station history; and steps less than 0.4°C are not adjusted since they are not often adequately identified by this or any other technique.

(...)

Figure 3 illustrates a typical station homogeneity assessment and adjustment situation. The annual mean minimum temperatures for Saint John, NB, are tested for homogeneity for the period 1895–1995. The series shows a decreasing linear trend of 2.4°C:101 years before adjustment (Figure 3(a)). Four steps are clearly identified by the procedure (Figure 3(b)). The step in 1961 results from the change of observing window which

produced a bias in the minimum temperature in 1961 at principal stations (described in the following section); the step in 1950 is associated with a site relocation with a 13-m increase in elevation; the step in 1947 is caused by the joining of two segments, Saint John and Saint John A in 1947; and finally the step in 1915 is caused by another site relocation with an increase in elevation of 9 m in 1914. **All of these steps are large enough to be adjusted with confidence without metadata support**, however, supporting history information was readily available to determine their causes. The adjusted series for Saint John, NB, shows a temperature increase of 0.2°C:101 years (Figure 3(c)), compared to a decrease of 2.4°C:101 years in the unadjusted series. Increasing linear trends of about this magnitude are also observed at neighbouring stations, and it is concluded that the adjusted series reflects more closely the temperature variations of the area.”

Section 2: Examples of quantified effects of non-climatic changes on measured temperature

As noted in the passages quoted in Section 1, there are many factors that could introduce non-climatic inhomogeneities into a temperature record. Some of these factors have been quantitatively studied in experiments or observational studies. The following tables list several key examples of studies that have quantified the effect on surface air temperature of changes to:

- a. Land use / land cover (LULC) characteristics in the environment surrounding the instruments (Table 1);
- b. The instruments themselves (Table 2);
- c. Observation or measurement procedures (Table 3).

Note that, in Table 1, some of the cited studies report the impact of environmental changes that occurred gradually. However, if the same environmental changes were to be implemented abruptly, they would necessarily give rise to an abrupt change in the temperature record. My purpose in presenting the references in Tables 1-3 is to show the magnitude of the impact of the different types of changes. The changes themselves can be abrupt even if they were gradual in the specific studies I’ve cited.

Table 1: Examples of quantified effect of land use / land cover (LULC) changes on surface air temperature

Type of LULC change	Proposed mechanisms by which change affects surface air temp.	Examples of quantified effect of change on surface air temp. Exp = Experimental study Obs = Observational study
Addition of buildings	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Reduction of sky-view factor - Shelter from wind - Shade - Increase of surface roughness affecting air flow 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Up to 1.2°C (0.5°C) increase in monthly mean minimum (maximum) at sheltered (“Test1”) site compared to reference site. (Brandsma, 2011) [Exp] - Up to 0.8°C mean difference in temperature between site closest to and furthest from built environment. (Leeper et al., 2019) [Exp] - 0.31°C (0.09°C) increase in minimum (maximum) temperature after local change to built environment (addition of building and parking lot, rerouted road) in early 2013 at Kingston, RI Climate Reference Network station. (Leeper et al., 2019) [Obs]

<p>Addition of pavement (parking lots, runways, roads, etc.)</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Different thermal conductivity and heat capacity than natural cover types like soil, sand, or grassland - Advection (horizontal movement of air warmed by pavement) - Change of albedo compared to natural cover, and pavement albedo changes as it ages from black to grey - Reduction of evaporating surfaces thus elevating sensible heating 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - 0.3°C (0.12°C) mean difference of daily minimum (maximum) temperature between site closest to and furthest from an asphalt car road at temperature measurement height of 2m. (Coppa et al., 2021) [Exp] - 0.2-0.4°C (0.1°C) mean difference of temperature between leeward and windward sides of an asphalt car road at temperature measurement height of 0.5m (1.5m). (Kumamoto et al., 2013) [Exp]
<p>Addition of trees, shrubs, bushes</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Reduction of sky-view factor - Shelter from wind - Shade - Increase of surface roughness affecting air flow 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Up to 0.6°C (0.4°C) decrease (increase) in monthly mean minimum (maximum) at test ("DB260") site near trees compared to reference site. (Brandsma, 2011) [Exp] - Mean nighttime air temperature substantially higher (>2°C) at shrubland site vs. grassland site in New Mexico desert. (He et al., 2010) [Obs]
<p>Changes to irrigation practices</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Irrigation increases soil moisture thus less sensible energy available for near surface warming 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - "Results show notably cooler temperatures over irrigated areas. For example, mean maximum growing season temperature at irrigated Alliance was 0.64°C and 1.65°C cooler compared to non-irrigated Halsey during pre- and post-1945 period, respectively." (Mahmood et al., 2006) [Obs] - "During [the July experimental period], on average, the mean daily temperature over irrigated areas was reduced by -0.69°C because of increased physical evaporation from soils and transpiration from crops." (Rappin et al., 2021) [Exp]
<p>Growth of nearby urban area ("urban heat island effect")</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Many factors affecting radiative and thermal properties of the ground and surface, and air movement, etc. due to replacing natural environment with streets, buildings, etc. (Oke, 2010). 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - 0.9°C increase over 80 years due to growth of local urban settlement toward the temperature sensor at Urbana, IL. (Changnon & Kunkel, 2006) [Obs] - 0.6°C increase over 45 years in urban development area of Vienna (Bohm, 1998). [Obs]

Table 2: Examples of quantified effect of instrumentation changes on surface air temperature

Type of instrumentation change	Proposed mechanisms by which change affects surface air temp.	Examples of quantified effect of change on surface air temp. Exp = Experimental study Obs = Observational study
Change from liquid-in-glass to resistance thermometers	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Thermometer “drift” in resistance thermometers (e.g. due to changes in the resistance-temperature relationship due to different thermal expansion coefficients of the sensing element and the substrate on which it is mounted) (Berry, 1982) - Column separations in liquid-in-glass thermometers causing erroneously high maximum and low minimum readings (Quayle et al., 1991) - Changes to the surroundings of the thermometer (such as the screen) when the thermometer is replaced (Quayle et al., 1991) 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - “The evaluated drift resulted in the order of 0.4°C, over 30 months of field measurements (figure 6). The exposure to low temperature and humidity showed similar values (figure 7).” (Merlone, 2021) [Exp] - “During the past five years, the National Weather Service (NWS) has replaced over half of its liquid-in-glass maximum and minimum thermometers in wooden Cotton Region Shelters (CRSs) with thermistor-based Maximum-Minimum Temperature Systems (MMTSs) housed in smaller plastic shelters. Analyses of data from 424 (of the 3300) MMTS stations and 675 CRS stations show that a mean daily minimum temperature change of roughly +0.3°C, a mean daily maximum temperature change of -0.4°C, and a change in average temperature of -0.1 °C were introduced as a result of the new instrumentation.” (Quayle et al., 1991) [Obs]
Change from manual to automatic weather stations	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Self-heating of thermometer from electrical components inside the instrument shelter - Changes to the surroundings of the thermometer (such as the screen) when the thermometer is replaced 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - “Self-heating in automatic weather stations originates not only from the temperature sensor itself but also from the electrical components housed together within. [...] In the study, the measured difference from the initial measured temperature was measured up to +0.32°C for currents compatible with modern dataloggers.” (Merlone, 2021) [Exp] - “The reported differences between the automatic and the manual measurements in side by side comparisons vary between ~ 0.1°C (Trewin, 2010) to up to 3°C (Bares & Mozny, 2014) [Exp] with the largest differences recorded on windless sunny days.” (Tsinko, 2016)
Change of screen type: adequacy of radiation shielding	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Whether screen properly shields radiation, including “back-radiation” reflected from the ground 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - “The experiment involved pairs of identical thermometers and shields, as commercially provided by manufacturers, including aspirated or naturally ventilated shields. Of the couples of identical sensors, one was positioned 2 m above snow covered soil

		<p>and the other 2 m above soil without presence of snow in the same site and in close vicinity, to guarantee same meteorological exposure [...] The effect under investigation was based on evaluating the differences among each couple of identical sensors. This was due to the overheating of the sensor above the snow, caused by the reflected radiation, hitting the shield from below. Results showed different amount of overheating, among the different typologies of instruments, ranging from about 0.5°C up to even 2.5°C, as shown in figure 5. As expected, the effect is evident only in daytime hours, while in the night the readings distribution is coherent with the overall calibration uncertainties of the various sensors.” (Merlone, 2021) [Exp]</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - “For the naturally ventilated screens/shields, a maximum positive Tdev of +3.4°C for AV-040(N) is seen from the influence of global solar radiation.” (Aoshima et al., 2010) [Exp] - “From our work, we can conclude that the temperature shift a [sic] average is of magnitude 0°C to +0.7°C when considering change in radiation shield type. [...] In case of temperature maximums, the shift can be up to +1.6°C in days with high global radiation (...)” (Bartokova et al., 2014) [Exp]
<p>Change of screen type: aging and repainting/repair</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Aging of screen exterior (e.g. yellowing of plastic or loss of paint), or repainting or repairing screen exterior following weathering. (Screen exterior should be highly reflective to prevent radiative warming of air passing over screen material before arriving at thermometer.) 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - “Lopardo et al. (2014) [Exp] looked at the age of AWS [automatic weather station] screens and found that the wearing off of the reflective coating can lead to significant differences of up to 1.63°C between the new and 5 year old screens.” (Tsinko, 2016)
<p>Change of screen type: airflow issues</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Change to airflow through screen (e.g. changing the type of naturally vented screen or changing from an “unaspirated” to an “aspirated” screen, etc.) 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - “van der Meulen & Brandsma (2008) [Exp] looked at ten different aspirated and non-aspirated screens including Stevenson type and found that differences can add up to 1°C and mainly result from the differences in air circulation speed and the response

		<p>time of various screens (van der Meulen & Brandsma, 2008).” (Tsinko, 2016)</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - “Naturally aspirated COOP sensors generally had warmer (+0.48°C) daily maximum and cooler (-0.36°C) minimum temperatures than USCRN, with considerable variability among stations.” (Leeper et al., 2015) [Obs] - “The field experiment was performed over a 1-year period to evaluate aspirated and non-aspirated Stevenson screen configurations used at the Meteorological Service of Canada’s Automated Weather Stations. The results show the non-aspirated screen is warmer than the aspirated screen duct location by 0.11°C on average with a significant increase in the maximum daily temperature of 0.22°C due to radiant heating effects. Temperature differences up to 2.1°C were observed between the aspirated and non-aspirated screens with a mean increase of 0.46°C following 30-min periods of mean global radiation greater than 200 W/m² and mean wind speed less than 2 m/s.” (Hoover & Yao, 2018) [Exp]
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Table 3: Examples of quantified effect of changes to observation methodology or procedures on surface air temperature

Type of change to observation methodology or procedure	Proposed mechanisms by which change affects surface air temp.	Examples of quantified effect of change on surface air temp. Exp = Experimental study Obs = Observational study
Change of observation time	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Poor timing of the 24-hour period over which maximum or minimum daily temperature is measured can introduce bias into the temperature record due to measuring the same (or similar) maximum or minimum across two measurement “days” (24-hour periods). 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - “The bias resulted from a nation-wide change in observing procedure at principal stations in 1961. [...] Annually, magnitudes [of the bias] were typically from 0.6 to 0.8°C in the east and much smaller at 0.2°C in the west.” (Vincent & Gullet, 1999) [Obs] - “We have shown that the TOB [time observation bias] in the United States can be quite large – as much as 2°C – and that the difference in biases, e.g., when the observation time changes from the late afternoon to near sunrise, is even greater.” (Karl et al., 1986)

<p>Change of algorithm for calculation of mean temperature</p>	<p>- Changing how daily “mean” temperature is calculated (e.g. average of daily max and min vs. average of several hourly measurements, etc.) can introduce a shift into a temperature record.</p>	<p>- “The algorithm used for the calculation of mean temperature will have an effect on longterm temperature measurements if there is a change from one algorithm to another [...] Victoria et al.⁵³ noted a shift of -0.18°C arising from a 1938 change in algorithm in Brazil. There have been a number of studies^{50,51,54–56} which have assessed systematic differences between two or more of the [mean calculation] methods described above. In general, these have found that differences tend to vary according to the nature of the location (...) and the season, but that differences between methods of 0.1–0.2°C on a network-wide basis, and 0.5–1.0°C at the most extreme individual sites, are typical.” (Trewin, 2010)</p>
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Section 3: Conclusion

There are thus many known physical causes of artifacts affecting surface air temperature measurements that can disrupt or bias a temperature record. Some of these artifacts can correspond to permanent shifts in mean annual temperature that can have magnitudes of the order of 1°C.

One can imagine possible changes to observation, measurement, or other procedures at the weather stations or in their immediate vicinities that could have produced the shift occurring at around 1998 in Eastern Canada stations. Examples include:

- deciding to base official temperature records on measurements from automatic weather stations rather than manual stations as of a certain date (even if the automatic stations were functional for some time prior to the switch-over date);
- upgrading or changing the type of temperature screen over the course of a year at many stations, e.g., by: implementing mechanical aspiration on all screens; refurbishing screen surfaces; replacing screens with a screen-type having inadequate back-radiation shielding; or other changes to screens;
- changing thermometer types, including associated electronics or other equipment;
- changing snow management practices or methods at airports introducing a local change of albedo;
- changing procedures at weather stations following an extreme weather event (e.g. the Ice Storm of 1998) to mitigate future damage, power outages, or other problems (an extreme weather event such as the 1998 Ice Storm could also affect the land use / land cover characteristics in the vicinity of the weather station and/or the instruments themselves);

and so on.

Section 4: List of References

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From: Vincent, Lucie (EC) <lucie.vincent@canada.ca>

Sent: June 25, 2021 2:53 PM

To: Joseph Hickey <JHickey@bank-banque-canada.ca>

Cc: Hartwell, Megan (EC) <megan.hartwell@canada.ca>; Wang, Xiaolan (EC) <xiaolan.wang@canada.ca>; Carou, Silvina (EC) <silvina.carou@canada.ca>

Subject: {External} FW: Bank of Canada's use of the 3rd Gen. AHCCD

CAUTION: This email comes from outside the Bank. Please exercise caution with external content and attachments. Contact Security if you have any concerns.

ATTENTION: Ce courriel provient d'une source extérieure. Prenez des précautions quand vous recevez des courriels qui ont du contenu externe et des pièces jointes. Si vous avez la moindre inquiétude, communiquez avec la Sécurité.

Hi Joseph,

I would like to confirm that the shift visually detected around 1998 in the time series of the annual mean temperature for the stations attached are not due to automation.

I quickly checked the metadata for some of the stations and I was not able to retrieve a date of change from manual to automated observations around 1998. Automation has been introduced gradually in Canada, from the early 1990s to the 2000s. In our studies, no systematic biases were found in daily temperature as result of automation as far as the instrumental systems were concerned. Based on a limited number of pair-sites, the Automatic Weather Observing System (AWOS) have shown slightly warmer temperatures, up to 0.2°C at some locations, due to un aspirated Stevenson screens, but now all screens are properly ventilated and they have been properly ventilated since many years.

Looking at temperatures from around the globe, we can see that the average temperature of the past decade (2011-2020) is definitively warmer than the previous decade (2001-2010), which is also warmer than the previous one (1991-

2000). The results of our studies regarding the temperature homogenization and trends are in agreement with the findings of other regions from around the globe.

I hope that this helps. Thank you for your interest in our work.

Lucie

Lucie A. Vincent

Research Climatologist / Climatologue chercheur
Climate Research Division / Division de la recherche climatique
Science and Technology Branch / Direction générale de la science et technologie
Environment and Climate Change Canada / Environnement et Changement climatique Canada
4905 Dufferin Street / 4905 rue Dufferin
Toronto, Ontario, Canada, M3H 5T4
Telephone / Téléphone : 416-739-4337
Facsimile / Télécopieur : 416-739-5700
Email / Courriel: Lucie.Vincent@canada.ca

From: Vincent, Lucie (EC)

Sent: June 24, 2021 11:47 AM

To: 'Joseph Hickey' <JHickey@bank-banque-canada.ca>; Hartwell, Megan (EC) <megan.hartwell@canada.ca>; Wang, Xiaolan (EC) <xiaolan.wang@canada.ca>

Cc: Tatjana Dahlhaus <tdahlhaus@bank-banque-canada.ca>

Subject: RE: Bank of Canada's use of the 3rd Gen. AHCCD

Hi Joseph,

Thank you for your enquiry. We will look into this issue and let you know. For now, we think that this issue is not related to the replacement of manual weather stations by automatic stations. But we will investigate this further.

We appreciate your comments and questions. Thank you.

Lucie

From: Joseph Hickey <JHickey@bank-banque-canada.ca>

Sent: June 24, 2021 8:49 AM

To: Vincent, Lucie (EC) <lucie.vincent@canada.ca>; Hartwell, Megan (EC) <megan.hartwell@canada.ca>; Wang, Xiaolan (EC) <xiaolan.wang@canada.ca>

Cc: Tatjana Dahlhaus <tdahlhaus@bank-banque-canada.ca>

Subject: Bank of Canada's use of the 3rd Gen. AHCCD

Category/Catégorie: Non-Sensitive/Non-Délicat

Dear Drs. Vincent, Hartwell, and Wang,

The Bank of Canada is using Environment and Climate Change Canada's 3rd Generation Adjusted and Homogenized Canadian Climate Data (AHCCD) in its policy and research work. I've been asked to write to you in the hope of clarifying a concern we have about the data.

While working with the AHCCD, we noticed a stepwise shift upwards of about 1 degree Celsius in magnitude occurring at around 1998 in the temperature records for several stations. The shift appears in plots of the yearly average of the AHCCD daily mean, max, or min temperature time-series. The same shift is also present in the raw data.

We would interpret that the sharpness in time and the magnitude of the shift are such that it must be of non-climatic origin. Also, I note that the shift occurs at a time when many manual weather stations were being replaced with automatic stations in Canada.

The magnitude of the shift is such that it could be the cause of all or most of the trend values that are extracted from this data by various researchers.

I explain these observations in more detail below, including several graphs I have made from the AHCCD data, which are in the attachment to this email.

We would appreciate any clarifications or guidance you might provide in understanding this aspect of the data, which appears to be an artifact.

Sincerely,

Joseph

--

Joseph Hickey, PhD

Data Scientist | Scientifique des données

Canadian Economic Analysis | Analyses de l'économie canadienne

Bank of Canada | Banque du Canada

jhickey@bank-banque-canada.ca

Yearly-averaged temperature plots for several stations in Eastern Canada

I have attached a PDF file to this email containing graphs of yearly-averaged temperature time-series for several AHCCD stations. Each row of graphs shows the data for a particular AHCCD station. In each row, the left graph shows the yearly-average of Tmean, and the centre and right graphs show the yearly-average of Tmax and Tmin, respectively. The Tmax, Tmin, and Tmean records are in degrees Celsius, and $Tmean = (Tmax + Tmin)/2$.

As an example, the top row of graphs in the attachment shows the yearly-averaged time series for Moncton. The AHCCD time-series for Moncton were constructed by joining a record from a downtown station (station ID: 8103100) spanning 1898-1939 with a record from the Moncton Airport (station ID: 8103200) spanning 1940-2012 and with a record from NavCan (station ID: 8103201) spanning 2012-2018 (Vincent et al., 2020). For Moncton, the AHCCD spreadsheet "Homog_max_temp_Inhomog_Causes.xls" (downloaded from the link [here](#)) indicates that an adjustment was made to the Tmax record in 1940 and that the potential cause was "Stations joined". The AHCCD spreadsheet "Homog_min_temp_Inhomog_Causes.xls" indicates that adjustments were made to the Tmin record at 1926, 1940, and 1961, with potential causes of "Reloc in 1926 to pumping station", "Stations joined", and "Change in obs time", respectively. These adjustments for Moncton are described further in Vincent et al. (2020). The AHCCD data for Moncton therefore contains no linking or homogenization adjustments for the period between 1961 and 2012.

As can be seen from the top row of plots in my attachment, the yearly-averaged Tmean, Tmax, and Tmin time-series for Moncton undergo an upward shift approximately 1 degree Celsius in magnitude at about 1998. Similar step-increase features at about 1998 are present in many other stations, as can be seen in my attachment. Additionally, for Moncton and some of the other stations in my attachment, the data segments for 1960-1997 and 1999-2020 appear to have roughly no trend.

Replacement of manual stations with automatic stations in 1992-2000

Vincent et al. (2020, at pg. 4) state that many stations in Canada underwent a change from manual to automatic observations between 1992 and 2000. Milewska and Vincent (2016, at pg. 34) give some additional information, as follows:

“In order to reduce the dependence of the RCS [reference climate station] network on third parties, Environment Canada initiated a climate network modernization project in 1996 (Yip et al., personal communication, 1999), in which continuity of records at vulnerable RCS stations was ensured through carefully managed systematic automation of the measurement programs. If no suitable nearby RCS replacement station was available, locations that were perceived at risk of closure in the future were automated using a tested, uniformly managed, standardized set of instruments. Some sites had already been automated prior to 1996 because more widespread automation aimed at streamlining operations had begun in the early 1990s. In 1998, a subset of 72 RCS stations was designated a part of Global Climate Observing System (Goodrich & Westermeyer, 2012) Surface Network (GSN). During the following years the list of RCS and GSN stations was further refined, and new automated stations were added in the North where no stations had previously existed.”

I do not have information that would allow me to know whether or not the specific stations for which I have shown graphs in my attachment converted from manual to automatic during this time period, but this information may be contained in the "metadata" for specific stations in the Canadian Climate Data Archives of Environment and Climate Change Canada.

Effect of a 1-degree upward shift on temperature trend

In yearly data spanning 1960-2019, just having a stepwise shift at 1998 is on its own enough to cause a rise equal to about 1.4 times the magnitude of the step, in a fit of a simple linear model. A rise of 1.4 (corresponding to a step of size 1 degree Celsius) is roughly equal to the trend values extracted from the AHCCD temperature data for many stations over 1960-2019, which are typically between 1-2 degrees in magnitude.

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L.A. Vincent, M.M. Hartwell, and X.L. Wang, “A third generation of homogenized temperature for trend analysis and monitoring changes in Canada’s climate”, *Atmosphere-Ocean*, iFirst article (2020) 1-19.

A Third Generation of Homogenized Temperature for Trend Analysis and Monitoring Changes in Canada's Climate

Lucie A. Vincent , Megan M. Hartwell & Xiaolan L. Wang

To cite this article: Lucie A. Vincent , Megan M. Hartwell & Xiaolan L. Wang (2020): A Third Generation of Homogenized Temperature for Trend Analysis and Monitoring Changes in Canada's Climate, Atmosphere-Ocean, DOI: [10.1080/07055900.2020.1765728](https://doi.org/10.1080/07055900.2020.1765728)

To link to this article: <https://doi.org/10.1080/07055900.2020.1765728>

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A Third Generation of Homogenized Temperature for Trend Analysis and Monitoring Changes in Canada's Climate

Lucie A. Vincent*, Megan M. Hartwell, and Xiaolan L. Wang

Climate Research Division, Science and Technology Branch, Environment and Climate Change Canada, Toronto, Ontario, Canada

[Original manuscript received 1 December 2019; accepted 30 March 2020]

ABSTRACT *This study presents the development of a new dataset of homogenized temperature for use in trend analysis and monitoring climate change in Canada. This dataset contains daily data for 780 locations across the country: 508 locations with an active station (current observations) and long record (starting prior to 1990); 53 locations with an active station and short record (starting after 1990); and 219 locations with no current observations (station closed) but with more than 30 years of data. Daily observations from nearby sites were often merged into a single record to create a long time series. This new dataset includes observations taken at Reference Climate Stations and from the Canada Aviation Weather Services, which are used to extend past climate observations into recent times. First, the data were quality controlled. The daily minimum temperature was adjusted for the change in observing time at principal stations in 1961. Parallel daily data were used to detect non-climatic shifts when the observations from nearby sites were merged. Series of annual and seasonal mean temperatures were tested for homogeneity. Daily temperatures were adjusted using a quantile-matching procedure if needed. Two main causes of data inhomogeneity affecting the trends over the 1948–2018 and 1900–2018 periods were identified. First, the change in observing time in 1961 introduced a cold bias in the annual means of the daily minimum temperatures after 1961. Second, merging observations from airport stations with older records has often created an artificial decreasing shift in the unadjusted data because of the better exposure of the instruments at airport stations. This new homogenized dataset shows a slightly stronger warming than the unadjusted data: the trend in the annual mean temperature for Canada has changed from 1.69° to 1.74°C for 1948–2018, and the trend for southern Canada has changed from 1.32° to 1.62°C for 1900–2018 because of all the adjustments applied to daily temperature in this study.*

RÉSUMÉ [Traduit par la rédaction] *Cette étude décrit la création d'un nouvel ensemble de données de température homogénéisées destiné à l'analyse des tendances et à la surveillance des changements climatiques au Canada. Cet ensemble contient les données quotidiennes de 780 sites canadiens: 508 stations actives (rapportent actuellement) possédant un long historique de relevés (commençant avant 1990); 53 stations actives possédant un court historique de relevés (commençant après 1990); et 219 sites sans observations actuelles (stations fermées), mais comptant plus de 30 ans de données. Dans plusieurs cas, nous avons fusionné les observations quotidiennes de sites voisins afin de créer une longue série temporelle unique. Ce nouvel ensemble de données comprend des observations prises aux stations climatologiques de référence ou par les Services météorologiques à l'aviation du Canada, et sert à prolonger les observations climatologiques passées jusqu'à des périodes récentes. Tout d'abord, les données ont fait l'objet d'un contrôle de qualité. La température minimale quotidienne a été changée pour tenir compte de la modification de l'heure d'observation dans les stations principales en 1961. Le chevauchement des données quotidiennes a servi à détecter les décalages non climatologiques lorsque les observations des sites voisins ont été fusionnées. Nous avons testé les séries de températures moyennes annuelles et saisonnières afin d'en vérifier l'homogénéité. Puis nous avons modifié les températures quotidiennes à l'aide d'une régression quantile, le cas échéant. Nous avons détecté deux causes principales d'inhomogénéité des données touchant les tendances sur les périodes de 1948 à 2018 et de 1900 à 2018: (1) la modification de l'heure d'observation en 1961, qui a généré un biais froid dans les moyennes annuelles des températures minimales quotidiennes après 1961; (2) la fusion des observations issues de sites aéroportuaires avec des relevés plus anciens, qui a souvent créé un décalage artificiel vers le bas des données non corrigées, en raison de l'exposition améliorée des instruments des sites situés aux aéroports. Ce nouvel ensemble de données homogénéisées montre un réchauffement légèrement plus important que les données non corrigées: la tendance de la température moyenne annuelle pour le Canada est passée de 1,69 à 1,74 °C pour la période de 1948 à 2018, et la tendance pour le sud du Canada est passée de 1,32 à 1,62 °C pour la période de 1900 à 2018, et ce, à la suite des modifications appliquées à la température quotidienne dans cette étude.*

*Corresponding author's email: Lucie.Vincent@canada.ca

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KEYWORDS climate change; climate trends; climate monitoring; surface air temperature; homogeneity testing; quantile-matching adjustments; Reference Climate Stations; Nav Canada stations

1 Introduction

Long records of climate observations at fine temporal and spatial resolution are needed for studying climate trends on local, regional, and global scales (Bush et al., 2014; Collins et al., 2014; Donat et al., 2013; Kirtman et al., 2013). High quality observations are also required in near-real time for monitoring the effects of climate change and extreme weather events on today's society (Blunden et al., 2018; WMO, 2018). In Canada, the climate monitoring network has experienced considerable changes over its long history of recording observations, particularly since the early 1990s. Programme reviews, including the modernization of the network with automated stations and the changing priorities of partner agencies who collect observations, have not only resulted in the closure of many long-term observing sites that had previously been in operation for decades but have also allowed for the installation of new sites in isolated areas. For this reason, it has become challenging for scientists to access long homogeneous records of climate observations that are routinely updated with current observations and can be used for studying climate trends in Canada.

Climate observations are stored in the National Climate Data and Information Archive and come from various private and public agencies and departments. The Meteorological Service of Canada (MSC) is responsible for archiving most of the climate observations recorded in Canada. A 7-digit climate identification number (denoted as climate ID or given by the actual 7-digit number hereafter) is assigned to a site where official weather observations are taken. This number serves as a unique identifier for retrieving climate data from the digital archives. When the observations are discontinued at a site because of site closure or a change in observing agency, for example, the same climate ID is not used for a subsequent site unless it is sufficiently close to the previous site, meaning that the observations can be

combined for use in some climatological applications. Climate observations can be taken by different instruments and agencies at the same location and stored under different climate IDs in the digital archives.

Reference Climate Stations (RCS) were identified in Canada in response to a request made by the World Meteorological Organization (WMO, 1986, 1993) that foresaw the need for continuous observations of temperature and precipitation for properly assessing climatic change. The WMO guidelines recommend that stations be chosen not only for the longevity of their climate data but also for their characteristics, that is, they should be permanent, well managed (with very few changes in instrumentation or observing procedures), and unaffected by densely populated areas. These stations should be protected from any changes, including closure, and satisfy specific climate research requirements, such as extending coverage to data sparse areas like the Arctic and the boreal region. As of today, about 300 stations have been assigned RCS status in Canada. Most RCS stations are operated by the MSC but some are from contributing agencies, such as the Aviation Weather Services and the Department of National Defense. Not all RCS stations have a long continuous record of climate observations: most of them have observations in near-real time but with a rather short record of 5–20 years of continuous data. The RCS stations and their compatibility with the US network is discussed in detail in Milewska and Vincent (2016).

In order to have a long time series of observations suitable for climate monitoring and trend analysis, climatologists have to join observations with different climate IDs and make the joined data series homogeneous (i.e., free of artificial non-climatic shifts). This is not a trivial task because consideration needs to be given to the climate conditions, location of instruments, observing procedures and agency, and the interval of time for which the observations were recorded; otherwise, results of climate trend studies could be biased by artificial non-climatic shifts in the data series. A typical example is given for North Battleford located in west-central Saskatchewan. As shown in Fig. 1, the daily temperatures from Battleford downtown (4040420; 1891–1942) were joined with those from North Battleford Airport (4045600; 1942–2005) located about 10 km from the previous site; this composite time series was further joined to the automated observations from North Battleford Airport (4045605; 2005–2010) and North Battleford RCS (4045607; 2010–2018) taken at the same location. In these situations, the joined data series should be checked to make sure that a non-climatic shift was not created at the joining dates, as in 1942, 2005, and 2010 in the North Battleford example.

In the mid-1990s, a First Generation Homogenized Temperature dataset was developed: it included long time series of homogenized monthly mean temperature at 210 locations

Fig. 1 Annual mean of the daily maximum temperatures from Battleford downtown station for 1892–1942 (blue); North Battleford Airport for 1942–2005 (red); North Battleford Airport automated observations for 2005–2010 (green), and North Battleford RCS automated observations 2010–2018 (magenta).

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(Vincent, 1998; Vincent and Gullett, 1999). This dataset was created for the analysis of temperature trends in Canada (Environment Canada, 1995; Zhang et al., 2000). In order to improve temporal and spatial coverage and benefit from newly developed techniques to adjust daily temperature data (Vincent et al., 2002; Wang et al., 2010, 2014), a Second Generation Homogenized Temperature was developed at the end of the 2000s, which included homogenized daily temperature at 338 locations (Vincent et al., 2012). This dataset has been updated every year with the most current observations and made available publicly on the Adjusted and Homogenized Canadian Climate Data (AHCCD) website (ECCC, 2018a). Annual, seasonal, and monthly mean temperature departures from the average of the 1961–1990 reference period were interpolated to evenly spaced grid points called Canadian Grid or CANGRD (ECCC, 2018b; Milewska and Hogg, 2001; Zhang et al., 2000) for ongoing monitoring of the regional and national temperature conditions presented in the *Climate Trends and Variations Bulletin* (ECCC, 2018c) and updates of the temperature trends in Canada (Vincent et al., 2015). The data were also used to analyze changes in indices based on daily and extreme temperatures (Vincent et al., 2018a; Vincent and Mekis, 2006) and one-in-20-year extreme temperature events at individual stations (Wang et al., 2014).

This paper presents the development of a Third Generation Homogenized Temperature, which builds on the Second Generation by first incorporating recent daily temperature observations taken at RCS sites and by the Aviation Weather Services (denoted as NavCan stations hereafter). Because many of the RCS sites have a relatively short period of data, it was often necessary to merge the RCS observations with those from the traditional older sites with longer records. To preserve the continuity of records during the modernization of the observing network, the MSC dedicated great effort

and expense to installing new RCS sites in close proximity to older sites to collect parallel observations (Milewska and Hogg, 2002; Milewska and Vincent, 2016; Vincent et al., 2018b). In this study, pair-sites data (parallel observations) are used, when available, to determine whether an artificial shift is created at the joining date when the observations of two sites are merged; these data are also used to estimate the adjustments needed to homogenize the data when necessary. Merging observations with RCS and NavCan sites addresses the decline of stations reporting daily temperatures in the Second Generation Homogenized Temperature (Fig. 2). The Third Generation also includes observations from new sites installed in isolated areas (mainly RCS sites that cannot be extended back in time to produce long records) and those from older sites that have collected observations for long periods of time (>30 years) but lack current observations for trend analysis.

In this study, the data were first quality controlled, and the daily minimum temperatures were adjusted for the change in observing time in 1961 at 96 principal (mainly airport) stations. Then, parallel daily observations derived from periods of overlapping data between joined stations were used to test for potential shifts. Series of annual and seasonal means of daily temperature were tested for homogeneity using the observations of neighbouring stations as reference series. Daily temperatures were adjusted using a quantile-matching procedure in order to diminish the shifts detected in the data time series: daily values prior to the detected shifts were adjusted to be in agreement with the most recent homogeneous segment of the tested series. Section 2 describes the data and methodologies used to develop the homogenized temperature dataset. In Section 3, the impact of the data inhomogeneities on the temperature trends are examined first for individual stations, then for Canada (1948–2018) and southern Canada (1900–2018). A discussion and concluding remarks follow in Sections 4 and 5, respectively.

Fig. 2 Number of locations reporting each year in the First Generation (green), Second Generation without any additional joined observations from the RCS and NavCan sites (red), and Third Generation Homogenized Temperature (blue). The Third Generation dataset contains homogenized daily temperature for 780 locations in total; however, this figure shows the 561 locations with current data; the 219 locations with no current observations and with a long record (>30 years) are not included.

2 Data and methods

a Data

Daily maximum and minimum temperatures (hereafter denoted by t_{max} and t_{min} , respectively,) were retrieved from the National Climate Data and Information Archive of Environment and Climate Change Canada. An inventory indicated that daily temperature can be retrieved for approximately 6350 different climate IDs. About 9% of the climate IDs have more than 60 years of data, 20% have 30–60 years, 47% have 5–30 years, and 24% have less than 5 years of data. The location with the longest record of “continuous” daily temperature (with very few missing values and the same climate ID) is Toronto, Ontario (6158350; 1840–2003) followed by Woodstock, Ontario (6149625; 1886–present), Calgary, Alberta (3031093; 1881–2012), Indian Head CDA, Saskatchewan (4013480; 1889–present), and Ottawa, Ontario (6105976; 1889–present). Other notably long records include Medicine Hat, Alberta (3034480; 1883–2008),

Montréal McGill, Quebec (7025280; 1871–1993), and Sable Island, Nova Scotia (8204700; 1897–present).

In this study, daily mean temperature (t_{mean} hereafter) is the average of t_{max} and t_{min} . Monthly mean maximum (or minimum) temperature is the average of t_{max} (or t_{min}) over the month and is set to missing if more than eight random or five consecutive daily values in the month are missing. Annual and seasonal means are calculated from the monthly values and retained if all related monthly values are non-missing. The seasons are defined as winter (December of the previous year to February of the current year), spring (March–May), summer (June–August), and autumn (September–November).

b Joining Observations for Co-Located Sites

In order to have a long time series that is useful for trend analysis, it was often necessary to merge observations from co-located sites or from the same site but archived under a different climate ID: co-located sites were usually in close proximity and most were not more than 10 km apart. Considerations were first given to all 300 RCS sites; their records were joined to the data of older sites, in particular, to those of the Second Generation of homogenized data, when possible. Then the remaining series from the Second Generation were extended to cover recent years, often with observations from NavCan stations. Finally, other sites with long records (>30 years) but with no current observations were considered for inclusion in the Third Generation. In this study, homogenized daily temperatures are developed for 780 locations and joining of a site's observations is done at many locations; more than half of the series are formed by joining the observations from two or more stations' records. Among the 780 locations, 33% (257) join two climate IDs, 17% (132) join three IDs, 7% (51) join four IDs, and 1% (8) join five IDs. There are 42% (332) remaining locations with single-station sites (no joining observations).

The number of joining dates per year shown in Fig. 3 has a peak over 1941–1945 and a second peak over 1965–1970. These dates generally correspond to the merging of observations from rural observing sites (located at houses or farms) to newly built airport stations (during the Second

Fig. 3 Number of joining dates per year in the Third Generation Homogenized Temperature.

World War, for example). In these situations, airport data are being extended backward in time using early climate stations. The third and fourth peaks over 1992–2000 and 2005–2008, respectively, are largely due to stations that have fully or partially ceased human observations: most of these sites were closed and then re-opened with automated observing systems and the data were stored under a different climate ID (some of these were assigned RCS status). The most recent peak over 2012–2015 mainly corresponds to joining dates with RCS and NavCan observations. In recent years, observations from RCS and NavCan sites have either been human or machine observations, or a combination of both, depending on the observing hours, specifically whether observations are made during evening, weekend, and holiday hours.

There are 224 locations with recent observations made at RCS sites whose data series were used to extend past climate observations into recent time (Fig. 4). There are 64 locations with recent RCS observations for which the data series were not joined in time because no sites with older daily temperature were available to use for joining (usually in remote areas). Currently, 12 of the 300 RCS sites are not included in the Third Generation because they have either too few observations or lack daily temperature observations. There are 48 locations with current data from NavCan stations that are not RCS sites (not all NavCan stations are used in this dataset) and 109 locations with data from the Second Generation that are not joined to RCS or NavCan sites.

Figure 5 indicates the locations of the 780 homogenized data series. There are 508 locations with an active station (current observations) and a long record (starting date prior to 1990). There are 53 locations with an active station and short record (starting date on or after 1990): these locations are mainly new RCS sites located in the North. Finally, there are 219 locations with no current observations (station closed) but with more than 30 years of data. These latest series cannot be used in trend analysis over 1900–2018 and 1948–2018; however, these homogenized data series can be used for other purposes, such as interpolating station data to an evenly spaced grid to compare observed data with model predictions.

c Checking Data Quality

A few basic checks were applied to ensure that the data were of reasonable quality. A suspicious daily temperature was identified when any one of the following criteria was met:

- t_{max} (or t_{min}) less than -60°C or greater than 50°C (this test was applied to identify outliers in the climate archives)
- t_{max} (or t_{min}) = 0 for more than five consecutive days (this happened at a few automated sites when the sensor was not reset properly)
- t_{min} is greater than t_{max} (t_{min} can be greater than t_{max} at airport stations where t_{min} and t_{max} were previously observed at different times)

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Fig. 4 Location of daily temperature observations at (a) 300 RCS sites (224 joined in time, blue; 64 not joined in time, green; 12 not used, red); (b) 48 NavCan sites (not RCS); (c) 109 Second Generation sites (not RCS, not NavCan); and (d) 335 remaining sites, for a total of 780 locations across the country.

Fig. 5 Location of the 780 homogenized data series. There are 508 locations with an active station (current observations) and long record (starting date prior to 1990, blue); 53 locations with an active station and short record (starting date from 1990, green); and 219 locations with no current observations (station closed) but with more than 30 years of data (red).

- the difference between t_{max} and t_{min} is greater than 40°C (either t_{max} or t_{min} could be wrong)
- t_{max} (or t_{min}) outside five standard deviations of the calendar day in question (the standard deviation was calculated for each calendar day using the full period of record).

The suspicious daily value was compared with the daily temperature before and after the identified day and sometimes with the observation at a nearby station. It was either retained, corrected (if the correction was obvious, such as the decimal point was at the wrong place or a negative sign was missing) or set to missing. Of the 780 homogenized data series of t_{max} and t_{min} throughout their complete period of record, only 0.0108% of data (about 2500 values) were identified as suspicious. About half were corrected or set to missing; the remainder were deemed accurate.

d Adjusting t_{min} for the Change in Observing Time in 1961

The highest and lowest temperatures are represented by t_{max} and t_{min} , respectively, over a 24-hour interval of time that does not necessarily correspond to the calendar day. On 1 July 1961, the climatological day (24-hour observing

window) was redefined to end at 0600 UTC (Universal Time Coordinated) at all principal stations (mainly airports) in Canada for both t_{\max} and t_{\min} (the non-airport stations did not have this change in observing time). Prior to that date, the climatological day ended at 1200 UTC for t_{\max} and 0000 UTC for t_{\min} . Because the 0600 UTC hour corresponds more closely to the time when the actual daily minimum temperature occurs (between midnight and dawn), it is now more likely that the same (or similar) minimum is recorded on two consecutive days, introducing a cold bias in the annual and monthly means of t_{\min} after July 1961 (Hopkinson et al., 2011; Vincent et al., 2009).

To resolve this bias (non-climatic shift), the affected t_{\min} were adjusted from July 1961 to present (here to 2018) using hourly temperatures (temperature observed at the top of the hour). An affected day was detected when the lowest hourly temperature in the 24-hour window ending at 0600 UTC was colder (by more than 0.5°C) than the lowest hourly temperature in the 24-hour window ending at 0000 UTC. For the affected day, t_{\min} was then estimated to be 0.5°C lower than the lowest hourly temperature in the 24-hour window ending at 0000 UTC: the subtraction of 0.5°C was used to estimate the small difference between the true daily minimum and the lowest hourly temperature (Hopkinson et al., 2011; Vincent et al., 2009). A similar approach was used to align the highest t_{\min} ; however, different highest values rarely occurred. Adjusting the period prior to 1961 (instead of after 1961) would have resolved the shift detected in the annual and monthly means of t_{\min} , but it would also have created “incorrect” t_{\min} before 1961 that do not correspond to actual minima in the daily temperature cycle.

In the current study, this procedure was applied to adjust t_{\min} at 96 principal stations because these stations were the only ones with sufficient hourly temperature observations (with few missing values) over the 1961–2018 period to properly identify the affected days. Because of the longitudinal width of Canada, the annual percentage of affected days gradually increases toward the eastern regions, from about

15% for stations in the west to 35% for stations in the east, over the 1961–2018 period. Therefore, the change in observing time in 1961 has created a larger bias in the annual and monthly means of t_{\min} at locations in the eastern regions where the minimum temperature occurs closer to 0600 UTC, and more days are affected by this observing time. The majority of the daily adjustments for the change in observing time in 1961 ranges from 0.5° to 5°C , and the average adjustment is 2.5°C . (Fig. 6).

e Detecting Shifts Using Parallel Observations at Pair-sites

The collection of parallel observations has gradually become standard practice in recent years in Canada. New RCS sites were installed in close proximity to traditional sites that had been operational longer with the purpose of collecting parallel observations (Milewska and Hogg, 2002; Milewska and Vincent, 2016). There are also a number of older sites where concurrent observations exist at pair-sites (old rural and airport sites for example), and these data were previously used for developing mathematical relations and validating daily temperature adjustments (Vincent et al., 2018b). In the current study, all pair-sites with parallel observations are used to determine whether a non-climatic shift is created at the joining date when the observations of two sites are merged. Not all pair-sites were closely co-located: most of the distances between the pair-sites were within 10 km and most of the elevation differences were within 30 m.

Annual and seasonal means of the daily temperature (t_{\min} or t_{\max}) were first computed at site 1 and site 2 separately using the parallel observations available (2–5 years) usually prior to the joining date. A t -test was applied to determine whether the difference between the means was statistically different from zero at the 5% significance level; 287 pair-sites were tested. Sometimes the difference between the pair-sites was statistically significant but of opposite sign in winter and summer and with a magnitude near zero in the annual means. A shift was retained if the difference in means was statistically different from zero in at least one season. Among all 287 pair-sites, 51 and 105 shifts were detected in the t_{\max} and t_{\min} series, respectively (42 shifts were detected for the same joining date in t_{\max} and t_{\min}). Among the 224 pair-sites when old records were merged to RCS sites, 37 and 56 shifts were identified in the t_{\max} and t_{\min} series, respectively, affecting less than 22% of these joining dates. Daily temperatures were adjusted using a quantile-matching algorithm (described in Section 2.g below) to diminish the shifts detected using parallel observations. All series were further tested for homogeneity using the observations of neighbouring sites as reference series.

f Detecting Shifts Using Neighbour's Observations as Reference Series

For each of the 780 locations, neighbouring sites were chosen (from the 780 locations) based on distance and periods of

Fig. 6 Frequency distribution of the adjustments applied to t_{\min} for the change in observing time in July 1961 at 96 principal stations. These adjustments were applied to the affected days from July 1961 to December 2018.

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available data. The 10 closest neighbours were identified with beginning and ending dates within 10 years of the tested series. Many of the neighbours in the southern regions of the country were within 20–100 km of the tested locations although they could be as far as 400 km apart in the north.

Annual and seasonal means were tested separately to ensure the detection of shifts in cases in which shifts of opposite magnitude were introduced in winter and summer. The penalized maximal *t*-test (PMTred) algorithm (Wang, 2008), as implemented in the RHtestsV4 package (Wang and Feng, 2009), was applied separately to the time series of the tested location using each neighbour site as a reference series. This algorithm searches for the most probable position of a shift in the difference (tested-minus-reference) time series and tests whether the shift is statistically different from zero at a chosen significance level (5% here) using a penalized maximal *t*-test (Wang et al., 2007). A reference series is needed to represent the trend and low-frequency variations in the tested series. A changepoint (date of a potential shift ± 1 year) was kept if it was detected in the annual series and in at least one season (or in the winter and summer series simultaneously). Because changepoints could arise from inhomogeneities in neighbour series (all neighbours were first adjusted for the change in observing time and shifts detected using parallel observations if needed), a changepoint was finally retained if it was detected using at least four neighbours to make sure that it would be attributable to the tested series (Trewin, 2013).

The available metadata were examined for all retained changepoints (shifts) to retrieve their potential cause. However, the station history files are often sparse and incomplete and do not routinely record all changes that have occurred at an observing site, especially the conditions surrounding the instruments, such as ground cover (e.g., pavement, grass) and construction of buildings. Still, greater confidence was placed in the data adjustments if the shifts were supported by some historical information.

The total number of retained shifts is reported in Table 1. It is important to mention that “no shifts” indicates that the tested series was found to be homogeneous at the 5% significance

level (i.e., no shifts were retained for adjustment because there was no agreement with the detection results provided by the 10 neighbours). About 72% (66%) of the tested series were declared homogeneous in their maximum (minimum) temperature series and do not need adjustment; one to four shifts were retained in the remainder of the tested series. Table 1 also provides the potential cause of the shifts that were kept for adjustment. About 72% (67%) of the shifts have an identified cause in their maximum (minimum) temperature series. The causes of these shifts include joining sites’ observations (the observations are from different climate IDs), relocation of the instruments, and other causes, such as changes in observer and surroundings (the observations are from the same climate ID). Many of the tested series that were declared homogeneous covered a relatively short period of time (<30 years); it is also possible that the interannual variability of the temperature in Canada, especially during the cold months, has made the detection of small inhomogeneities more difficult.

g Adjusting Daily Temperature Using a Quantile-matching Algorithm

The quantile-matching (QM) algorithm as described in Wang et al. (2014) was used for adjusting the shifts detected using parallel observations at pair-sites (first approach) and those detected using neighbour observations as reference (second approach). Both approaches are described in detail in Vincent et al. (2018b) and summarized as follows.

In the first approach, the daily temperature at site 1 and site 2 taken over the overlapping period of two to five years (usually prior to the joining date) are used for developing the daily temperature’s adjustments. The quantiles (1st, 2nd, 3rd, ... percentiles) of all data over the overlapping period are obtained for site 1 and site 2 separately; the quantiles are binned into 12 categories, and 12 quantile-category means are calculated for each site. The difference in the category-mean between the two sites is obtained, and a natural spline is fitted to the 12 category-mean differences. The daily adjustment is estimated as the value of the fitted spline corresponding to the quantile of the value to be adjusted.

In the second approach (using a neighbour’s data series as reference), the daily tested-minus-reference values (differences) are first obtained. These daily differences are binned into 12 categories according to the quantile of the corresponding value in the tested series. Such quantile-category binning is done for the segment of data over the five years before and five years after the shift to be adjusted (the year with the shift is not included). Then, for each quantile-category, the difference in the category-mean between the segments of data before and after the shift is obtained. A natural spline is fitted to the 12 category-mean differences. The daily adjustment is estimated as the value of the fitted spline corresponding to the quantile of the value to be adjusted. The three neighbours with the same identified shift and having the highest correlation with the tested series were used to

TABLE 1. (a) Number of tested series with zero, one, two, three, and four shifts, which have been adjusted, for maximum and minimum temperature; (b) number of shifts due to different causes.

	Maximum temperature	Minimum temperature
(a) No. of series with		
no shifts	564 (72.3%)	514 (65.9%)
one shift	126 (16.3%)	145 (18.6%)
two shifts	58 (7.4%)	78 (10.0%)
three shifts	19 (2.4%)	29 (3.7%)
four shifts	13 (1.6%)	14 (1.8%)
total no. of stations	780	780
(b) No. of shifts due to		
joining observations	121 (34.5%)	132 (29.7%)
relocation	69 (19.7%)	83 (18.7%)
other causes	63 (17.9%)	82 (18.5%)
no cause found	98 (27.9%)	147 (33.1%)
total no. of shifts	351	444

produce three sets of daily adjustments: the final adjustment of the daily value was the median of the adjustments derived from the three neighbours.

In the current work, all adjustments are taken to occur on 1 January unless the month with the shift is identified from the metadata, joining dates, or previous work. The daily temperatures prior to the detected shifts are adjusted to be in agreement with the most recent homogeneous segment of the tested series. The majority of the QM adjustments range from -3° to 2° C, with an average of -0.2° C for t_{\max} , and from -3.5° to 2.5° C, with an average of -0.4° C for t_{\min} (Fig. 7).

h *Example of Detecting Shifts Using Parallel Observations at Pair-Sites*

The daily temperatures at Victoria Gonzales Hts, British Columbia (1018610; 1898–1973) were joined with those at Victoria Int'l Airport (1018620; 1974–2013) located 27 km from the previous site; this composite series was further joined to the observations at Victoria Int'l Airport (1088621; 2013–2018) taken by NavCan. Victoria Gonzales Hts is located in a coastal hilly area with an elevation of 70 m, with trees and buildings surrounding the observing site, and is in close proximity to Juan de Fuca Strait. The instruments located at Victoria Int'l Airport are at 20 m elevation, far from water, and have better surface air exposure than at Victoria Gonzales Hts (trees and buildings are far from the instruments). Daily temperatures were observed simultaneously at both locations from 1974 to 1978, and these observations were used to determine if an artificial shift was created at the joining date in 1974.

The difference between the daily temperatures over the 1974–1978 period (Victoria Int'l Airport minus Victoria Gonzales Hts) shows substantial variability and a strong seasonal pattern (Figs 8a and 8b). Victoria Gonzales Hts is more affected by the winds than Victoria Int'l Airport because it is in close proximity to a large body of water. Close examination of the seasonal means of the daily differences reveals that the t_{\max} values for Victoria Int'l Airport are generally warmer than those observed at Victoria Gonzales Hts, especially during the summer, by an average of about 1.9° C (Fig. 8c). This is probably a result of the instruments at the airport being located at lower elevation and far from the cooling effect of trees. However, the t_{\min} values for Victoria Int'l Airport are much colder than those observed at Victoria Gonzales Hts, especially in the winter, spring, and autumn, by an annual average of 1.8° C (Fig. 8d). Because the instruments at the Victoria Gonzales Hts site are surrounded by trees and buildings, the nighttime temperature does not cool as much as the nighttime temperature at the airport, which has better exposure.

To diminish the shift in the composite daily temperature series, the QM adjustment for each daily temperature value was derived from the spline fitted to the 12 quantile-category means of the differences between the two sites (Figs 8e and 8f). As a result, the summer high values of t_{\max} at Victoria Gonzales Hts are adjusted by approximately 2.1° C, and the

winter low values of t_{\min} are adjusted by approximately -3° C. The daily adjustments have increased the annual mean of t_{\max} by about 0.7° C prior to 1974 (Fig. 8g), while they have decreased the annual mean of t_{\min} by about 1.8° C (Fig. 8h). The composite series of the annual mean of t_{\min} was also adjusted for the change in observing time in 1961, and the adjustments have increased the annual mean of t_{\min} by an average of 0.4° C for the 1974–2018 period. After all these adjustments, the annual mean of t_{\max} (t_{\min}) shows an increasing trend of 0.5° C (1.9° C) from 1900 to 2018, which is of a similar magnitude to the trends observed at neighbouring sites over a comparable period of time.

i *Example of Detecting Shifts Using Neighbour's Observations As Reference Series*

The daily temperatures at Moncton, New Brunswick (8103100; 1898–1939) were joined with those at Moncton Airport (8103200; 1940–2012) located 11 km from the previous site; this composite series was further joined to the NavCan observations at Moncton Int'l Airport (8103201; 2012–2018). The instruments at Moncton were located downtown near buildings and trees at an elevation of 12 m. The instruments at the airport have a higher elevation of 71 m and better air exposure with no trees or buildings surrounding the instruments. Parallel observations are not available for this location.

The composite series of the annual and seasonal means of daily temperature were tested for homogeneity using 10 neighbours separately. The difference in the annual mean of t_{\max} (t_{\min}) between the tested series (Moncton composite series) and a neighbour (Fredericton, located 180 km from Moncton, used here as an example) indicates change points detected in 1926 and 1940 (Figs 9a and 9b). These change points are identified with at least three other neighbouring series (same date ± 1 year). The year 1926 corresponds to the relocation of the instruments to the pumping station, three blocks away from the former site, with a change in observer; the inspector's report made several years after the relocation reveals that the instruments were not relocated to an adequate location. The year 1940 is associated with the joining of observations from the Moncton downtown site to the airport.

The seasonal mean difference (5-years-after-1940 minus 5-years-before-1940) of the daily differences between the tested series and neighbour indicate that the t_{\max} (t_{\min}) observations made at the airport are, on average, about 0.5° C (0.7° C) colder than those from the pumping station although the difference in t_{\min} is more pronounced in winter and spring (Figs 9c and 9d). This difference in temperature is likely a result of the location of the instruments at the airport, with a higher elevation and better exposure.

To diminish the shift in 1940, the QM adjustment for each daily temperature value was derived from the spline fitted to the 12 quantile-category-mean differences shown in Figs 9e and 9f. As a result, most t_{\max} values at the Moncton pumping station are adjusted by approximately -0.5° C during the 1926–1939 period. The winter low t_{\min} values

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Fig. 7 Frequency distribution of the QM adjustments applied to (a) tmax and (b) tmin. These adjustments were applied from the beginning of the record to the date of the more recent shift at each station with identified inhomogeneities.

are adjusted by about -1.0°C while the summer high tmin values are adjusted by about -0.1°C over the same period. The daily adjustments have decreased the annual mean of tmax (tmin) by approximately 0.5°C (0.7°C) over the 1926–1939 period. The procedure is repeated to derive the adjustment for the change point in 1926, which is combined with the adjustments for the 1940 shift to lower the data before 1926. These adjustments decreased the annual mean of tmax (tmin) by about 0.2°C (0.5°C) during the 1900–1925 period (Figs 9g and 9h). The composite series of annual mean of tmin was also adjusted for the change in observing time in 1961, and these adjustments have increased the annual mean of tmin by an average of 0.7°C over the 1961–2018 period. No adjustments were applied to tmin between 1940 and 1961. After all adjustments, the annual mean of tmax (tmin) shows an increasing trend of 1.6°C (2.4°C) from 1900 to 2018, which is in agreement with the trends observed at neighbouring stations over a similar period.

3 Impact of data inhomogeneities on trends in temperature

Because very few stations in the northern regions have climate observations prior to 1948, temperature trends are examined for two periods: 1948–2018 for all stations across Canada to provide a national assessment and 1900–2018 for the stations located mainly in the south for a longer perspective (more than 100 years). The methodology to calculate the trends follows the approach described in Zhang et al. (2000) and Wang et al. (2006). The estimated magnitude of the trend is based on the slope estimation from Sen (1968), and its statistical significance is obtained from the nonparametric Kendall's tau test (Kendall, 1955). This approach was used to assess the trends in Canada's climate (Vincent et al., 2015) and in temperature and precipitation indices (Vincent et al., 2018a).

a Impact on Trends at Individual stations

Trends in annual and seasonal means of tmax and tmin are obtained before and after adjustments at individual stations. A station's trend is missing when more than 10% of consecutive years or more than 20% of random years are missing,

where the percentage is calculated from the length of the analyzed period. The trends were computed at 250 (75) individual stations for the period 1948–2018 (1900–2018). The adjustments either “increase” the trend (the difference in the magnitude of the trends “after minus before adjustments” is positive) or “reduce” the trend (the difference in the magnitude of the trends is negative) at individual stations (Fig. 10). For 1948–2018, the adjustments increase the trends in the annual mean of tmax (tmin) at 18% (53%) of the stations while they reduce the trends at only 10% (12%) of the stations. During 1900–2018, the trends in the annual mean of tmax (tmin) increased at 38% (73%) of the stations, whereas they were reduced at 16% (11%) of the stations with the adjustments. Trends in the seasonal mean of tmax and tmin show similar results. Overall, more stations have an “increased” trend than a “reduced” trend with the adjustments, particularly for tmin and the longer 1900–2018 period. In other words, stronger warming is detected at many stations when the adjustments are applied, especially for tmin over the 1900–2018 period. Still, the difference between the trends shows a random pattern of changes (Fig. 10), and the adjustments have not artificially created regional warming.

To investigate the causes of data inhomogeneity affecting the trends, the positive and negative adjustments for the stations reporting trends for the 1948–2018 and 1900–2018 periods are classified into six categories based on their cause (Fig. 11). The categories are defined as follows: change in observing time in 1961 (for tmin only); data joined to RCS sites; data joined to other sites (mainly airports and other agencies); relocation of the instruments; other causes identified (including changes in observers and surroundings); and no identified causes.

The main cause of data inhomogeneity affecting the trends for 1948–2018 and 1900–2018 is the change in observing time in July 1961. Adjustments were applied at principal stations to resolve the cold bias introduced in the annual and monthly means of the daily minimum temperatures after 1961 (green bars in Figs 11b and 11d). Another important cause of data inhomogeneity affecting the trends is the merging of observations from airports to older sites (light blue bars in Fig. 11). The instruments were often originally located in

Fig. 8 Differences in (a) tmax and (b) tmin between the two sites (Victoria Int'l Airport minus Victoria Gonzales Hts); (c) and (d) seasonal means, and (e) and (f) 12 quantile-bins mean of the differences; (g) and (h) annual mean series before (dotted line) and after (solid line) applying the adjustments. In (e) and (f), the horizontal axis is the percentile, and the dotted line represents the spline fitted to the 12 quantile-bins mean.

backyards near pavement and buildings with poor air exposure, and merging these observations to airport stations often created an artificial decreasing shift in the unadjusted data because of the better exposure of the instruments at airport stations. The adjustments resulting from these two main causes have generally accentuated the warming trend at individual stations.

Merging observations from RCS to older sites sometimes created a shift in the unadjusted temperature series because of the change in the instrument's location (darks blue bars in Fig. 11). No shift was detected as a result of joining

observations to NavCan sites because the instruments remained at the same location and elevation, most of the time.

Some of the adjustments applied during the 1901–1930 period, classified as relocation, other causes, and no identified cause (brown, grey, and black bars in Figs 11c and 11d), likely coincide with the introduction of the Stevenson screen. Original temperature screens were often mounted on an independent wall or on the north wall of a building, and they were gradually replaced by the Stevenson screen at the beginning of the twentieth century (Devine, 2006). It is very difficult to retrieve this information from the historical files, but it is

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Fig. 9 Differences in annual mean of (a) tmax and (b) tmin between the tested series (Moncton) and neighbour (Fredericton); (c) and (d) seasonal mean and (e) and (f) 12 quantile-bin mean differences (5-year-after-1940 minus 5-year-before-1940) in the daily Moncton-minus-Fredericton series; and (g) and (h) the annual mean series before (dotted line) and after (solid line) applying the adjustments. In (a), (b), (g), and (h), the vertical lines represent the dates of the detected shifts (1926 and 1940). In (e) and (f), the horizontal axis is percentile, and the dotted line represents the spline fitted to the 12 quantile-bins mean.

sometimes possible to speculate on the replacement of the screen when old photos are available.

b Impact on Canada's Trends (1948–2018)

Because stations recording temperature observations are not uniformly distributed across the country, with more stations in the south and fewer in the north, temperature data were interpolated to evenly spaced point locations for a better spatial assessment of the climate variations. Annual and seasonal temperature anomalies from the 1961–1990 reference

period were first obtained at individual stations. They were then interpolated to 50 km–spaced grid points using Gandin's Optimal Interpolation method (Alaka and Elvander, 1972; Bretherton et al., 1976; Gandin, 1965). The main prerequisite for a location to participate in the gridding process was having a 1961–1990 average. Therefore, the number of locations contributing to the gridding process increased from 338 locations (Second Generation) to 576 locations (Third Generation); however, most of the new contributing locations were found south of 60°N. The number of locations participating in the gridding process will increase if the reference period

Fig. 10 Difference in the magnitude of the trends (after minus before adjustment) in annual mean of tmax and tmin temperature for the two periods analyzed.

(here 1961–1990) changes (to 1981–2010 for example) because more locations, particularly in the North, have data over the more recent time period. Grid point values were averaged to produce a time series, at annual and seasonal resolution, representing the entire country for 1948–2018, and southern Canada (south of 60°N) for 1900–2018. A trend value was computed at each grid point and for the national and southern time series. The statistical significance of the trend was assessed at the 5% level.

The new homogenized data show warming across the country during the 1948–2018 period. Significant trends in annual mean temperature ranging from 1° to 3°C are found almost everywhere across the nation (Fig. 12a). The

warming is more pronounced in the northern regions, especially in the Yukon, Northwest Territories, and western Nunavut, where trends greater than 3°C are observed in some areas over the past 71 years. The warming is slightly greater in the annual tmin than in the annual tmax, particularly in the western regions (figures not shown). Visually, the maps of temperature trends derived from the new homogenized data do not show strong differences from those produced from the unadjusted data (figures not shown). The national time series computed from the homogenized data exhibits considerable variability although a steady increase is observed from the beginning of the 1970s to the 2000s (Fig. 12b). This new homogenized dataset shows a slightly stronger warming in Canada

TABLE 2. Trends in annual and seasonal means of tmax, tmin, and tmean for Canada as a whole 1948–2018 (°C per 71 yr), and for southern Canada 1900–2018 (°C per 119 yr) before and after adjustments, respectively. The “y” (“n”) indicates a trend statistically significant (not significant) at the 5% level. Trends with a difference (after minus before adjustments) >0.2°C are in bold to highlight the greatest changes.

Region	Period	Season	tmax before	tmax after	tmin before	tmin after	tmean before	tmean after
Canada	1948–2018	Annual	1.62y	1.58y	1.70y	1.92y	1.69y	1.74y
		Winter	2.96y	3.01y	3.39y	3.56y	3.20y	3.30y
		Spring	1.62y	1.53y	1.59y	1.74y	1.58y	1.56y
		Summer	1.37y	1.30y	1.36y	1.54y	1.37y	1.45y
		Autumn	1.48y	1.45y	1.49y	1.67y	1.50y	1.56y
Southern Canada	1900–2018	Annual	1.00y	0.99y	1.68y	2.29y	1.32y	1.62y
		Winter	1.86y	1.85y	2.68y	3.53y	2.19y	2.70y
		Spring	1.15y	1.15y	1.65y	2.23y	1.39y	1.67y
		Summer	1.03y	0.98y	1.73y	2.08y	1.37y	1.54y
		Autumn	0.51n	0.51n	1.18y	1.76y	0.81y	1.09y

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Fig. 11 Number of positive and negative adjustments for the stations reporting trends in (a) tmax for 1948–2018; (b) tmin for 1948–2018; (c) tmax for 1900–2018; and (d) tmin for 1900–2018, for six categories and four periods. The categories are change in observing time in 1961 (green); data joined to RCS sites (dark blue); data joined to other sites (light blue); relocation of the instruments (brown); other identified causes (grey); no identified causes (black).

compared with the unadjusted data, with an increase in annual mean temperature of 1.74°C for the 1948–2018 period, whereas an increase of 1.69°C was found in the unadjusted data (Table 2). The adjustments have slightly decreased the trend in annual tmax (from 1.62° to 1.58°C), whereas they have increased the trends in annual tmin (from 1.70° to 1.92°C) over the last 71 years.

Seasonally, the greatest warming is experienced during the winter (Fig. 13). The winter warming trends are predominant in the western regions and the northern regions ranging from 4° to 6°C over the past 71 years in most areas. During the spring, the warming is less pronounced, but significant warming trends are also dominant over the western regions. Summer mean temperature has increased less than the winter and spring mean temperatures, but the magnitude of the warming is consistent across the country. In autumn, most of the warming is observed in the Arctic and northern Quebec. Here again, the maps of the seasonal trends derived from the homogenized data are not very different visually

from those produced from the unadjusted data. Seasonal mean temperature anomalies averaged over Canada indicate significant increases of 3.30°, 1.56°, 1.45°, and 1.56°C from 1948 to 2018 for winter, spring, summer, and autumn, respectively (Table 2). The adjustments have slightly changed the magnitude of the seasonal trends and the greatest change is found in tmin. Annual and seasonal temperature trends and their spatial patterns across the country obtained over the 1948–2018 period produced from the Third Generation data are similar to those produced using the Second Generation data over a similar period 1948–2012 (Vincent et al., 2015).

c Impact on Southern Canada's Trends (1900–2018)

The new homogenized data show pronounced warming across southern Canada for the 1900–2018 period (Fig. 14). The warming is less evident in annual tmax, which indicates no significant increasing trends in some areas of the western provinces, as well as in Ontario and Quebec; it is more

Fig. 12 Trends in (a) annual mean of tmean for 1948–2018 ($^{\circ}\text{C}$ per 71 yr). Grid squares with trends statistically significant at the 5% level are marked with a dot. (b) Annual mean of tmean anomalies for Canada, 1948–2018. The red line indicates the anomalies before adjustment, and the black line is an 11 yr running mean.

pronounced in annual tmin showing significant increasing trends of 1° to 3°C across the region. The adjustments have not considerably changed the spatial pattern of the trends (figures not presented here). The annual tmean averaged over southern Canada has increased by 1.62°C during the 1900–2018 period (Table 2). The adjustments have not changed the trend in annual tmax (about 1.0°C for 1900–2018), but the trend in annual tmin has changed from 1.68° to 2.29°C for the same period.

The adjustments have increased the trends in tmin by more than 0.2°C in every season over the past 119 years (Table 2). The greatest change in trends is found in the winter tmin (from 2.68° to 3.53°C after adjustment). As mentioned previously, the change in trends in annual and seasonal tmin is mainly a result of the adjustments for the change in observing time after 1961 and for the joining of observations from sites with poor air exposure to sites with better air exposure, effectively removing any insulating effects (meaning that the nights are generally colder at recent sites). As a result, the unadjusted annual tmin time series for southern Canada shows an obvious warm bias prior to 1970 (Fig. 14d). The spatial pattern of the temperature trends and the magnitude of the trends obtained over the 1900–2018 period with the Third Generation data are generally in agreement with the findings produced using the Second Generation data over a similar period 1900–2012 (Vincent et al., 2015).

4 Discussion

It is difficult to determine the exact cause of an artificial shift in temperature time series because it often corresponds to confounding changes occurring at the same time. For example, a relocation of the instruments, even a few metres away from the original site, often coincides with the screen being cleaned or repainted, new thermometers installed, observers re-instructed about practices, and different surroundings. The station's history files, frequently based on inspectors' reports, do not often document the changes occurring at the

observing site but instead record the instruments used, location, observers, and surroundings on specific dates; some stations have only a few inspectors' reports during their long record of observations. A combination of many causes can amplify or cancel their impact on daily temperature, and it becomes very difficult to classify the magnitude of the detected inhomogeneities by cause. In the current study, the cause of the detected shifts was mainly the result of a major change in the instrument's exposure, often associated with a change in location and elevation.

Microclimatic inhomogeneities can also be introduced in temperature datasets as a result of growth or removal of surrounding vegetation, construction of roads and buildings, and maintenance of instruments and their shelters (Runnalls and Oke, 2006). Although these are a source of uncertainty in long-term temperature records, it is often difficult to properly detect microclimatic inhomogeneities because it requires the observations of a nearby and reliable neighbour station (no more than a few kilometres away and with no inhomogeneities) and detailed knowledge of the station's history (often not available). In addition, the growth of surrounding vegetation or of a nearby town can introduce a gradual artificial trend in the temperature time series and not an artificial shift. More work is needed to develop procedures to properly detect and adjust these inhomogeneities when possible: these inhomogeneities were rarely recognized in the current work.

Automatic weather stations (electronic observing systems with sensors relating weather data to a data logger without human involvement) were widely introduced across the Canadian network from the early 1990s onward. In some cases, their introduction coincided with a station move and a period of parallel observations. Overall, no systematic biases were found as a result of automation as far as the instrumental systems were concerned. Based on a limited number of pair-sites, the Automatic Weather Observing Systems (AWOS) have shown slightly warmer temperatures, up to 0.2°C , because of the un aspirated Stevenson screen being cluttered with additional devices (Milewska and Hogg, 2002). At

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Fig. 13 Trends in (a) winter, (c) spring, (e) summer, and (g) autumn tmean for 1948–2018 ($^{\circ}\text{C}$ per 71 yr). Grid squares with trends statistically significant at the 5% level are marked with a dot. Tmean anomalies for (b) winter, (d) spring, (f) summer, and (h) autumn for Canada, 1948–2018. The red line indicates the anomalies before adjustment, and the black line is an 11 yr running mean.

Fig. 14 Trends in annual mean of (a) tmax, (c) tmin, and (e) tmean for 1900–2018 (°C per 119 yr). Grid squares with trends statistically significant at the 5% level are marked with a dot. Annual mean of (b) tmax, (d) tmin, and (d) tmean anomalies for southern Canada, 1900–2018. The red line indicates the anomalies before adjustment, and the black line is an 11 yr running mean.

RCS sites, the largest bias came from matching the time of observations, while a small siting bias was due to differences in landscape, vegetation, and elevation when the sites were not exactly collocated (Milewska and Vincent, 2016). There is now less clutter on RCS screens and many have become aspirated (Ewa Milewska personal communication, 2018). Similar to Canada, the introduction of automated systems has not created a bias in temperature series in Australia (Trewin, 2013).

Homogenization of daily temperatures with regard to climate extremes is still an important topic for further studies. Several methods have been developed for adjusting not only the mean of a daily temperature time series but also its higher-order quantiles (Della-Marta and Wanner, 2006; Kuglitsch et al., 2009; Mestre et al., 2011; Toreti et al., 2010; Trewin, 2013). A recent study has indicated that the QM approach (Wang et al., 2014) can provide a good estimate of the adjustments when indices of extreme

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temperature are computed from homogenized daily values and the adjustments are based on highly correlated neighbours (Vincent et al., 2018b). An approach based on wavelet analysis has also demonstrated progress in quantifying daily temperature adjustments when dealing with climate extremes (Li et al., 2014; Yan and Jones, 2008). Nonetheless, more work is required to improve methodologies for the homogenization of daily temperature extremes.

5 Concluding remarks

The climate monitoring network in Canada has undergone considerable changes over its long history of recording observations. Many long-term observing stations were closed, and new sites were opened in isolated areas. The Third Generation Homogenized Temperature incorporates recent daily temperature observations made at RCS and NavCan stations. These data were used to continue in time the observations from older sites that had been operational longer in order to create long series for use in climate trend studies. Parallel observations were used, when available, to determine whether an artificial shift was created at the joining date when the observations from two sites were merged. Furthermore, the annual and seasonal time series for all stations were tested for homogeneity using neighbour observations as a reference series.

One of the main causes of data inhomogeneity affecting the trends over the 1948–2018 and 1900–2018 periods was the change in observing time in July 1961 at principal stations, which introduced a cold bias in the annual means of the daily minimum temperatures after 1961. Another important cause of data inhomogeneity affecting the trends corresponded to the merging of observations from airport stations to older records which often created an artificial decreasing shift in the unadjusted data because of the better exposure of the instruments at airport stations. The adjustments resulting from these two main causes have accentuated the warming trend at individual stations. Merging observations from older records with those from the RCS sites has created a shift in the unadjusted temperature series in fewer than 22% of the cases, often the result of differing instrument locations. This new homogenized dataset shows a slightly stronger warming in Canada and southern Canada than the unadjusted data. Because of the adjustments, the trend in the annual mean temperature in Canada has changed from 1.69° to 1.74°C for the 1948–2018 period, and the trend in southern Canada has changed from 1.32° to 1.62°C over the longer 1900–2018 period.

The homogenized daily temperatures from the Third Generation and Second Generation can be different at similar locations for three main reasons. First, merging observations from sites was carried out differently in the Third Generation to extend long records of daily data to recent time with the

observations from the RCS and NavCan stations (if needed). Second, homogeneity testing was done over a longer period of time in the Third Generation which includes an additional 18 years of data: shifts could have been detected in the recent years and earlier data adjusted to correct these newly detected shifts. Third, the adjustments were derived from three neighbouring sites in the Third Generation instead of from the highest correlated site as done in the Second Generation. This was done in order to minimize the influence of outlying daily temperature values that can be found at an individual neighbour station. The most difficult task in homogeneity assessment is to choose the correct number of shifts and concurring dates because different neighbours frequently provide different changepoints. It was often necessary to compare the trends with the surrounding sites after adjustment over similar periods in order to gain some confidence in the adjustments. If the resulting trend was very different from those computed at surrounding sites then the number of shifts and concurring dates were re-assessed and adjustments were applied accordingly.

It is very important to document all adjustments made to the data and to preserve the original observations for a better understanding of the impact of the adjustments on various climate applications. Proper documentation is also crucial for assisting users' understanding of the limitations of the datasets and to ensure accurate interpretation of the results derived from the data. In the current study, the impact of the data adjustments on the trends for 1948–2018 and 1900–2018 was examined in detail. More work is still needed to assess the impact on record daily high and low temperatures at individual stations and to make sure that the extremes are properly adjusted. The selection of the sites to be joined and joining dates was done following the best knowledge of the authors at the time of the study; however, these can be revised in the future to better integrate the experience of local climatologists and accommodate future changes in the climate network. The original and adjusted series along with the station list, sites joined including climate IDs and periods of time, and potential causes of the adjusted shifts (when known), are available from the authors and will be available on the Government of Canada's Open Data Portal.

Acknowledgements

The authors would like to thank the internal reviewers Mark Barton, Marc Beauchemin, Bridget Thomas, Giselle Bramwell, and Pamela Lehr (MSC), as well as two anonymous reviewers, for their helpful comments and suggestions that have helped to improve the manuscript.

Disclosure statement

No potential conflict of interest was reported by the author(s).

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Hartwell, Megan (ECCC)

From: Julien McDonald-Guimond <JMcDonald-Guimond@bank-banque-canada.ca>
Sent: June 25, 2020 11:50 AM
To: Vincent, Lucie (ECCC)
Subject: RE: Inquiry about your paper "Changes in Canada's Climate: Trends in Indices Based on Daily Temperature and Precipitation Data"

Category/Catégorie: Non-Sensitive/Non-Délicat

Thank you for those precisions Lucie. It's consistent with what I had in mind.

For strictly continuous series like average temperature the procedure was obvious, but I was uncertain regarding those series where we essentially count a number of days per year, thus leaving zeros here and there. Often times it's almost easier to visually assess if there's a trend or not (for instance, if the zeros are concentrated at the beginning or at the end, excluding them can have a big impact).

Have you considered fitting trends based on a different assumption for the shocks, such as a Poisson distribution?

All the best,
Julien

De : Vincent, Lucie (EC) <lucie.vincent@canada.ca>
Envoyé : 25 juin 2020 11:39
À : Julien McDonald-Guimond <JMcDonald-Guimond@bank-banque-canada.ca>
Objet : {External} RE: Inquiry about your paper "Changes in Canada's Climate: Trends in Indices Based on Daily Temperature and Precipitation Data"

Bonjour Julien,

We are calculating the trend using two methods: the best-fit linear trend and the trend estimated on the median of the slopes. This is done for all stations and all indices. Both values are often very similar.

In the case of hot days, the time series can have many zeros, mainly for stations in the northern part of the country. In this situation, the zeros can be replaced by missing values (so they are not included in the trend calculation). If the trend based on the median is similar to the best-fit linear trend then we have more confidence in the results (we checked if both trends were statistically significant). However, if a time series has too many zero values, it is sometime preferable not calculating the trend at all.

I hope this helps.

Lucie

From: Julien McDonald-Guimond <JMcDonald-Guimond@bank-banque-canada.ca>
Sent: June 23, 2020 5:48 PM
To: Vincent, Lucie (EC) <lucie.vincent@canada.ca>
Subject: RE: Inquiry about your paper "Changes in Canada's Climate: Trends in Indices Based on Daily Temperature and Precipitation Data"

Category/Catégorie: Non-Sensitive/Non-Délicat

Bonjour Lucie,

I have a possibly simple yet important question regarding the slope estimator that you use in your analyses of trends. I have read Sen (1968) as well as the paper by Zhang et al., but I still can't confirm the following.

Can the estimator be used with a lot of zero observations, or should these points be removed?

For instance, when studying threshold-based indices (e.g. hot days), you mention that only stations with at least five excess years are kept. This means that many years must have had zeros. Did you run the usual estimator on those data directly or do the zeros need to be removed?

As you can imagine, since the estimator is based on the median, not removing the zeros makes it very likely that the estimate will be zero. But is ignoring the zeros valid?

Thank you very much for your guidance,
Julien

De : Vincent, Lucie (EC) <lucie.vincent@canada.ca>

Envoyé : 21 mai 2020 2:43

À : Julien McDonald-Guimond <JMcDonald-Guimond@bank-banque-canada.ca>

Objet : {External} RE: Inquiry about your paper "Changes in Canada's Climate: Trends in Indices Based on Daily Temperature and Precipitation Data"

s.19(1)

Bonjour Julien,

I am glad that you were able to get the homogenized daily temperature. We have been working on a Third Generation of Homogenized Temperature that will be available in a near future. We have a paper on the third generation that will be published in Atmosphere-Ocean soon.

Please find enclosed our paper on the Second Generation Homogenized Temperature, Trends in Canada's climate and Trends in climate indices. I checked in emails regularly and will be happy to answer your questions if I can.

All the best,

Lucie

From: Julien McDonald-Guimond <JMcDonald-Guimond@bank-banque-canada.ca>

Sent: May 13, 2020 3:12 PM

To: Vincent, Lucie (EC) <lucie.vincent@canada.ca>

Subject: RE: Inquiry about your paper "Changes in Canada's Climate: Trends in Indices Based on Daily Temperature and Precipitation Data"

Category/Catégorie: Non-Sensitive/Non-Délicat

Bonjour Mme Vincent,

Apologies for the double-email. I simply wanted to let you know that in the mean time a colleague of yours, Vincent Cheng, was able to help me out. I reached out to the general contact email regarding technical difficulties in downloading the monthly homogenized data, and he was able to point me to the [daily frequency repository](#).

That said, I would be more than happy to keep the communication channels opened between us, if this is agreeable to you. This way we could share knowledge and help advance this important research agenda.

Best,
Julien

De : Julien McDonald-Guimond

Envoyé : 13 mai 2020 2:21

À : Lucie.Vincent@canada.ca

Objet : Inquiry about your paper "Changes in Canada's Climate: Trends in Indices Based on Daily Temperature and Precipitation Data"

Category/Catégorie: Non-Sensitive/Non-Délicat

Bonjour Mme Vincent,

I hope this email finds you well. My colleagues and I are currently working towards a research agenda linking long-term changes in weather and economic outcomes in Canada. We have examined your recent paper on temperature and precipitation trends and have found it quite insightful. The coverage and clarity of the work greatly helped us getting an overview of the situation in Canada.

In your paper, you reference a dataset of daily homogenized weather data which appears robust to many changes that happened through time. I looked around in search of this dataset but was only able to find one with data at monthly frequency. Would you happen to know if it is available elsewhere or if it can be accessed on a special basis?

I thank you very much in advance for your time,
Julien

p.s. I would be more than happy to correspond in French if it is also your preferred language.

Julien Mc Donald-Guimond

Économiste | Economist

Section des études sur l'économie canadienne | Canadian Economic Studies Division

Analyse de l'économie canadienne | Canadian Economic Analysis

234 rue Wellington Street, Ottawa ON K1A 0G9

Téléphone | Telephone : 613.782.7083

JMcDonald-Guimond@bank-banque-canada.ca

Hartwell,Megan (ECCC)

From: Julien McDonald-Guimond <JMcDonald-Guimond@bank-banque-canada.ca>
Sent: May 25, 2020 8:29 AM
To: Vincent, Lucie (ECCC)
Subject: RE: Inquiry about your paper "Changes in Canada's Climate: Trends in Indices Based on Daily Temperature and Precipitation Data"

Category/Catégorie: Non-Sensitive/Non-Délicat

Good morning Lucie,

It is great to hear that you are still investing energy into research

We have started exploring the data and it is encouraging to see that the patterns are close to what we were getting using basic rules for station aggregation. The thorough work done to produce the homogenized data will allow us to focus more on the analysis and less on the methodological considerations of weather measurement, which is clearly within ECCC's expertise. The extension of the temporal dimension is also something very useful to us.

We'll make sure to go over the papers that you shared. We also accept your generous offer to answer our questions!

Have a great week,
Julien

De : Vincent, Lucie (EC) <lucie.vincent@canada.ca>
Envoyé : 21 mai 2020 2:43
À : Julien McDonald-Guimond <JMcDonald-Guimond@bank-banque-canada.ca>
Objet : {External} RE: Inquiry about your paper "Changes in Canada's Climate: Trends in Indices Based on Daily Temperature and Precipitation Data"

Bonjour Julien,

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All the best,

Lucie

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Best,
Julien

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Envoyé : 13 mai 2020 2:21

À : Lucie.Vincent@canada.ca

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I thank you very much in advance for your time,
Julien

p.s. I would be more than happy to correspond in French if it is also your preferred language.

Julien Mc Donald-Guimond

Économiste | Economist

Section des études sur l'économie canadienne | Canadian Economic Studies Division

Analyse de l'économie canadienne | Canadian Economic Analysis

234 rue Wellington Street, Ottawa ON K1A 0G9

Téléphone | Telephone : 613.782.7083

JMcDonald-Guimond@bank-banque-canada.ca

Changes in Canada's Climate: Trends in Indices Based on Daily Temperature and Precipitation Data

L.A. Vincent, X. Zhang, É. Mekis, H. Wan & E.J. Bush

To cite this article: L.A. Vincent, X. Zhang, É. Mekis, H. Wan & E.J. Bush (2018): Changes in Canada's Climate: Trends in Indices Based on Daily Temperature and Precipitation Data, Atmosphere-Ocean, DOI: [10.1080/07055900.2018.1514579](https://doi.org/10.1080/07055900.2018.1514579)

To link to this article: <https://doi.org/10.1080/07055900.2018.1514579>

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Changes in Canada's Climate: Trends in Indices Based on Daily Temperature and Precipitation Data

L.A. Vincent*, X. Zhang, É. Mekis, H. Wan, and E.J. Bush

*Climate Research Division, Science and Technology Branch,
Environment and Climate Change Canada, Toronto, Ontario, Canada*

[Original manuscript received 19 February 2018; accepted 7 July 2018]

ABSTRACT Trends in indices based on daily temperature and precipitation are examined for two periods: 1948–2016 for all stations in Canada and 1900–2016 for stations in the south of Canada. These indices, a number of which reflect extreme events, are considered to be impact relevant. The results show changes consistent with warming, with larger trends associated with cold temperatures. The number of summer days (when daily maximum temperature $>25^{\circ}\text{C}$) has increased at most locations south of 65°N , and the number of hot days (daily maximum temperature $>30^{\circ}\text{C}$) and hot nights (daily minimum temperature $>22^{\circ}\text{C}$) have increased at a few stations in the most southerly regions. Very warm temperatures in both summer and winter (represented by the 95th percentile of their daily maximum and minimum temperatures, respectively) have increased across the country, with stronger trends in winter. Warming is more pronounced for cold temperatures. The frost-free season has become longer with fewer frost days, consecutive frost days, and ice days. Very cold temperatures in both winter and summer (represented by the 5th percentile of their daily maximum and minimum temperatures, respectively) have increased substantially across the country, again with stronger trends in the winter. Changes in other temperature indices are consistent with warming. The growing season is now longer, and the number of growing degree-days has increased. The number of heating degree-days has decreased across the country, while the number of cooling degree-days has increased at many stations south of 55°N . The frequency of annual and spring freeze–thaw days shows an increase in the interior provinces and a decrease in the remainder of the country. Changes in precipitation indices are less spatially coherent. An increase in the number of days with rainfall and heavy rainfall is found at several locations in the south. A decrease in the number of days with snowfall and heavy snowfall is observed in the western provinces, while an increase is found in the north. There is no evidence of significant changes in the annual highest 1-day rainfall and 1-day snowfall. The maximum number of consecutive dry days has decreased, mainly in the south.

RÉSUMÉ [Traduit par la rédaction] Nous examinons les tendances d'indices fondés sur les températures et les précipitations quotidiennes pour deux périodes : de 1948 à 2016, pour toutes les stations au Canada, et de 1900 à 2016, pour les stations du sud du pays. Ces indices, dont certains représentent des événements extrêmes, sont considérés comme pertinents sur le plan des impacts. Les résultats montrent des changements en accord avec un réchauffement et des tendances prononcées associées à des températures froides. Le nombre de jours estivaux (lorsque la température quotidienne maximale $> 25^{\circ}\text{C}$) a augmenté à la plupart des sites au sud de 65°N , et les nombres de jours chauds (température quotidienne maximale $>30^{\circ}\text{C}$) et de nuits chaudes (température quotidienne minimale $>22^{\circ}\text{C}$) ont augmenté à quelques stations, dans les régions les plus au sud. Les températures très chaudes, tant en été qu'en hiver (représentées respectivement par les 95e centiles des températures maximales et minimales quotidiennes), ont augmenté partout au pays, avec des tendances plus fortes en hiver qu'en été. Le réchauffement est plus prononcé dans le cas des températures froides. La saison sans gel s'est allongée: il y a aussi moins de jours de gel, de jours de gel consécutifs et de jours sans dégel. Les températures très froides, tant en hiver qu'en été (représentées respectivement par les 5e centiles des températures maximales et minimales quotidiennes), ont augmenté considérablement partout au pays, encore une fois avec des tendances plus fortes en hiver qu'en été. L'évolution d'autres indices de température concorde avec un réchauffement. La saison de croissance s'est allongée et le nombre de degrés-jours de croissance a augmenté. Les degrés-jours de chauffe ont diminué dans l'ensemble du pays, tandis que les degrés-jours de refroidissement ont augmenté à de nombreuses stations au sud de 55°N . Les fréquences annuelles et printanières des jours de gel-dégel montrent une augmentation dans les provinces centrales et une diminution dans le reste du pays. L'évolution des indices de précipitations est moins cohérente sur le plan spatial. Nous constatons une hausse du nombre de jours avec pluie et forte pluie à plusieurs endroits dans le sud. Nous observons une baisse des nombres de jours avec chute de neige et forte chute de neige dans les provinces de l'ouest, et une augmentation dans le nord. Il n'y a aucune

*Corresponding author's email: Lucie.Vincent@canada.ca

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preuve de changements significatifs de la quantité quotidienne de pluie ou de neige la plus élevée sur une année. Le nombre maximal de jours secs consécutifs a diminué, principalement dans le sud.

KEYWORDS climate change; climate trends; climate indices; daily temperature; daily precipitation; temperature extreme; precipitation extreme

1 Introduction

Canada's climate is changing. Surface air temperature has risen; spring precipitation has been shifting from snow to rain; and the duration of snow cover has been decreasing (Brown, Derksen, & Wang, 2010; Mekis & Vincent, 2011; Vincent et al., 2015). The directions of change are consistent with what would be expected from a warming climate, and many of the observed trends are projected to continue into the future under scenarios of further emissions of greenhouse gases (Bush, Loder, James, Mortsch, & Cohen, 2014; Collins et al., 2013; Kirtman et al., 2013; Seneviratne et al., 2012). Canada is a vast country, and changes in Canada's climate are not spatially uniform. In addition, climate trends in Canada are not temporally consistent. Therefore, it is important to closely monitor changes in temperature and precipitation conditions using long-term climate data in order to determine whether the trends continue when reliable data for more locations and longer periods of time become available.

Canada is becoming warmer. The annual mean temperature averaged over land has increased by 1.7°C from 1948 to 2012 (Vincent et al., 2015). Although warming occurs everywhere across the country, stronger trends were found during winter and spring in western and northern regions. Daily minimum temperatures have been rising slightly faster than daily maximum temperatures (Vincent et al., 2012). Canada's precipitation has also increased. The increase in precipitation amounts is dominated by large changes observed in British Columbia, southern Ontario, southern Quebec, and Atlantic Canada (Mekis & Vincent, 2011). Snowfall amounts have decreased in southern regions of the country from British Columbia to southern Quebec, while they have increased in Atlantic Canada and in the north (north of 60°N). These changes in temperature and precipitation conditions have led to a shorter snow-cover season, mainly in response to earlier snowmelt resulting from warmer spring temperatures (Brown et al., 2010; Mudryk et al., 2018).

A changing climate can have both positive and negative effects on Canada's communities and economies (Warren & Lemmen, 2014). Some regions could benefit from milder and shorter winters because this could diminish the demand for heating buildings and thus reduce energy consumption. Fewer extreme cold days and frost days could result in easier conditions for road transportation and fewer weather-related injuries. A longer growing season could be beneficial for agriculture, and more summer days could result in an extended outdoor recreational season. However, a warmer climate is also associated with an increase in the frequency of hot days and hot nights that can adversely affect the health and well-being of Canadians (Casati, Yagouti, &

Chaumont, 2013). Warmer temperatures are generally accompanied by less snowfall, and less snow on the ground can reduce winter activities and have a negative impact on agriculture because of lower water availability (Blankinship & Hart, 2012).

Several studies have already examined trends in indices based on daily and extreme temperature and precipitation in Canada. Data coverage for the entire country has been available since 1948. Fewer cold nights, cold days, and frost days and conversely more warm nights, warm days, and summer days were found across the country (Vincent & Mekis, 2006). Trends in the 5th and 95th percentiles of the daily maximum and minimum temperatures show fewer days with extreme low temperatures and more days with extreme high temperatures (Bonsal, Zhang, Vincent, & Hogg, 2001). The number of growing and cooling degree-days has increased, whereas the number of heating degree-days has decreased (Bonsal et al., 2001). There has been a significant lengthening of the growing season because of an earlier start and a later end to the season (Qian, Zhang, Chen, Feng, & O'Brien, 2010). Fewer freeze-thaw days were found in southern Quebec (Yagouti, Boulet, Vincent, Vescovi, & Mekis, 2008). More days with precipitation and a decrease in the maximum number of consecutive dry days have been observed for Canada (Vincent & Mekis, 2006). No consistent trends were found in extreme precipitation, whereas increases in total precipitation have been found, mainly because of an increase in the number of small to moderate precipitation events (Zhang, Hogg, & Mekis, 2001). These results for Canada are in general agreement with global-scale studies that have indicated widespread warming trends in temperature indices and changes in precipitation indices that are spatially more complex but show a tendency toward wetter conditions (Donat et al., 2013).

The purpose of this study is to present an updated analysis of the trends in indices based on daily temperature and precipitation for monitoring climate change impacts in Canada. It updates some of the previous work presented in Vincent and Mekis (2006), Bonsal et al. (2001), and Zhang et al. (2001) by using the latest version of the homogenized daily temperatures and adjusted daily precipitation, now available at more locations, and by examining the trends over a longer period of time, which includes at least an additional 10 years of recent data. The indices were selected for their relevance to social and economic impact assessment in Canada and for the insights they could provide regarding changes in extreme climate conditions. Historical changes are also useful benchmarks for evaluating climate models. In this paper, the trends are first examined at individual

Trends in Indices Based on Daily Temperature and Precipitation Data / 3

stations and then they are analyzed for six sub-regions as well as the entire country. Section 2 describes the data and methodologies. The trends are presented in Section 3. Section 4 provides a discussion of the relevance of these changes to the health of Canadians and to some of the important sectors of the Canadian economy (e.g., tourism, agriculture, energy, and shipping). A summary and conclusions follow in Section 5.

2 Data and methodologies

a Temperature Indices

The temperature indices were computed from homogenized daily maximum and minimum temperatures at 338 locations across the country (Vincent et al., 2012). Homogeneity issues related to station relocation, changes in observing time, and joining of observations from co-located sites were addressed using regression models and the observations of neighbouring stations (Vincent, Zhang, Bonsal, & Hogg, 2002; Wang, Feng, & Vincent, 2014). A set of 21 temperature indices was selected for this study (Table 1). Some of these indices are based on fixed thresholds (e.g., summer days) because these are easily understood; however, they may not be applicable in every region of the country (e.g., hot days are rare in the Arctic). Other indices are based on percentiles (e.g., 95th percentile of the daily maximum temperature) to facilitate the comparison of long-term changes between different climatic regions. Some of the indices are computed on an annual basis and others on a seasonal basis (Table 1). Monthly values are set to missing when the values for more than three consecutive days or more than five random days are missing in the month; annual and seasonal values are missing when the value for any month is missing in the year or season.

The indices describe warm and cold conditions along with other climatic conditions that are impact relevant, such as frost-free season, growing season, degree-days, and freeze-thaw days. The threshold of 25°C is used to define summer days because warm-weather seasons can be beneficial to Canadian tourism (Kovacs & Thistlethwaite, 2014). Thresholds of 30°C and 22°C are chosen to define hot days and hot nights, respectively, and, along with the summer 95th percentile of the daily temperatures, were used by Health Canada experts to characterize the occurrence of warm-weather events that can result in negative outcomes for Canadian communities (Casati et al., 2013). Frost days, consecutive frost days, ice days, and the winter 5th percentile of the daily temperatures are used to characterize cold conditions. The length of the frost-free season is important to agriculture and shipping (Andrey, Kertland, & Warren, 2014). A daily mean temperature above 5°C was chosen to define the growing season and growing degree-days, which are important indicators of crop viability (Bootsma, Anderson, & Gameda, 2011). Cooling and heating degree-days can be used to evaluate energy consumption (Instanes, 2005). Degree-days are based on departures of the daily mean temperature from a threshold (Table 1), which are summed on a yearly basis to determine the annual number of degree-days. Freeze-thaw days can have a significant effect on road maintenance (Hershfield, 1979; Ho & Gough, 2006; Schmidlin, Derthier, & Eggleston, 1987) and can play an important role in the production of maple syrup in Ontario and Quebec (Duchesne, Houle, Côté, & Logan, 2009; Pothier, 1995). In this study, the 95th and 5th percentiles of the daily temperature are often referred to as very warm and very cold days, respectively; the daily minimum and maximum temperatures are also referred to as the nighttime and daytime temperatures, respectively.

TABLE 1. Definition of the temperature indices.

Conditions	Indices	Definitions	Period
Warm	Summer days	Number of days with $t_{max} > 25^{\circ}C$	Jan-Dec
	Hot days	Number of days with $t_{max} > 30^{\circ}C$	Jan-Dec
	Hot nights	Number of days with $t_{min} > 22^{\circ}C$	Jan-Dec
	95th perc. t_{max}	95th percentile of t_{max}	Sum & Win
	95th perc. t_{min}	95th percentile of t_{min}	Sum & Win
Cold	Frost days	Number of days with $t_{min} \leq 0^{\circ}C$	Jul-Jun
	Consecutive frost days	Maximum number of consecutive days with $t_{min} \leq 0^{\circ}C$	Jul-Jun
	Ice days	Number of days with $t_{max} \leq 0^{\circ}C$	Jul-Jun
	5th perc. t_{max}	5th percentile of t_{max}	Win & Sum
	5th perc. t_{min}	5th percentile of t_{min}	Win & Sum
Frost-free season	Frost-free season (FFS)	Maximum number of consecutive days with $t_{min} > 0^{\circ}C$	Jan-Dec
	FFS starting date	Frost-free season starting date	Jan-Jun
	FFS ending date	Frost-free season ending date	Jul-Dec
Growing season	Growing season (GS)	Number of days between starting and ending dates	Mar-Nov
	GS starting date	Date when $t_{mean} > 5^{\circ}C$ for 6 consecutive days	Mar-Jun
	GS ending date	Date when $t_{mean} < 5^{\circ}C$ for 6 consecutive days	Jul-Nov
Degree-days	Growing degree-days (GDD)	Sum of degrees when $t_{mean} > 5^{\circ}C$	Jan-Dec
	Cooling degree-days (CDD)	Sum of degrees when $t_{mean} > 18^{\circ}C$	Jan-Dec
	Heating degree-days (HDD)	Sum of degrees when $t_{mean} < 18^{\circ}C$	Jul-Jun
Freeze-thaw days	Annual freeze-thaw days	Number of days with $t_{min} \leq 0^{\circ}C$ and $t_{max} > 0^{\circ}C$	Jan-Dec
	Spring freeze-thaw days	Number of days with $t_{min} \leq 0^{\circ}C$ and $t_{max} > 0^{\circ}C$	Jan-Apr

Note: T_{max} , t_{min} , and t_{mean} are daily maximum, minimum, and mean temperatures, respectively. Period indicates when the index is calculated: for example, "Jan-Dec" is for January to December; "Jul-Jun" is for July of the previous year to June of the current year; "Sum & Win" is for summer (JJA) and winter (DJF).

TABLE 2. Definition of the precipitation indices.

Conditions	Indices	Definitions	Period
Wet	Days with rainfall	Number of days with rainfall ≥ 1 mm	Jan-Dec
	Days with snowfall	Number of days with snowfall ≥ 1 mm	Jul-Jun
	Days with precipitation	Number of days with precipitation ≥ 1 mm	Jan-Dec
Very wet	Days with heavy rainfall	Number of days with rainfall >90 th percentile	Jan-Dec
	Days with heavy snowfall	Number of days with snowfall >90 th percentile	Jul-Jun
	Days with heavy precipitation	Number of days with precipitation >90 th percentile	Jan-Dec
Highest	Highest 1-day rainfall	Highest 1-day rainfall during the year	Jan-Dec
	Highest 1-day snowfall	Highest 1-day snowfall during the year	Jul-Jun
	Highest 1-day precipitation	Highest 1-day precipitation during the year	Jan-Dec
Dry	Maximum number of consecutive dry days (MCDD)	Maximum number of days with daily precipitation $<$ trace	Jan-Dec

Note: Period indicates when the index is calculated: for example, “Jan–Dec” is for January to December; “Jul–Jun” is for July of the previous year to June of the current year.

b Precipitation Indices

The precipitation indices were computed from daily rainfall, daily snowfall, and daily total precipitation amounts at 464 stations across the country. Daily total precipitation (called daily precipitation hereafter) is the sum of the daily rainfall and snowfall water equivalent amounts. These data have been adjusted to address known measurement issues (Mekis & Vincent, 2011). Daily rainfall was corrected for wetting losses associated with different types of manual rain gauges used in the past (Devine & Mekis, 2008). Daily snowfall, taken from snow ruler measurements, were converted to appropriate snow water equivalent amounts (Mekis & Brown, 2010). Adjustments for trace observations (smaller than the minimum measurable amount) were also added to daily rainfall and snowfall depending on the station location and measurement program (Mekis & Hogg, 1999; Mekis & Vincent, 2011). A set of 10 precipitation indices was chosen for this study (Table 2).

The indices describe wet, very wet, highest 1-day events, and dry conditions. A threshold of 1 mm was chosen (instead of zero or trace) to identify days with rainfall, snowfall, and precipitation because trace observations have not been recorded consistently in time and across the country. However, it is important to note that trace observations are important for properly computing precipitation accumulation on a monthly or seasonal basis, especially in dry regions like the Arctic. For very wet conditions, the 90th percentile

reference value was calculated from all daily events greater than or equal to 1 mm within the 1961–1990 period and the number of days with rainfall, snowfall, and precipitation above their respective 90th percentiles was obtained each year. The highest 1-day rainfall, snowfall, and precipitation amounts were retrieved each year to provide some insights into changes in extreme precipitation amounts. The maximum number of consecutive dry days was calculated using daily total precipitation less than the trace amount to characterize the length of dry spells. Similar to the temperature indices, the monthly values, and consequently the annual values, were set to missing when the value for precipitation was missing for more than three consecutive days or more than five random days in a given month.

c Trend Estimation

Because very few stations in the northern regions reported climate observations prior to 1948, trends in temperature and precipitation indices were first examined for two time periods: 1948–2016 for all stations to provide a national picture and 1900–2016 for stations in the south for a longer perspective. The trends were computed for stations with less than 10% missing years in the respective periods. Figure 1 shows the number of stations for which trends could be calculated: it decreases after 2005 mainly because of the downsizing of the traditional manual observing network and the introduction of

Fig. 1 Number of stations that reported trends in (a) temperature and (b) precipitation indices during the 1948–2016 period (blue) and 1900–2016 period (red). The vertical black dashed line indicates the year 2012.

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automated systems (Milewska & Vincent, 2016). Because the reduction in the number of stations with precipitation trends is substantial after 2012 (also shown in Mekis et al., 2018), the trends for the precipitation indices were re-computed for the shorter periods 1948–2012 and 1900–2012.

The trend calculation followed the methodology presented in Zhang, Vincent, Hogg, and Niitsoo (2000). The estimated magnitude of the trend is based on the slope estimator of Sen (1968), and the statistical significance of the trend is based on the nonparametric Kendall's τ -test (Kendall, 1955). Because serial correlation is occasionally present in the climatological time series, the method also uses an iterative procedure to account for the lag-1 autocorrelation of the time series (Wang & Swail, 2001). Trends were computed for individual stations, and the statistical significance of the trends was assessed at the 5% level. Trends for threshold-based indices (e.g., number of hot days) were computed only for stations where the temperature threshold is exceeded regularly (for at least five years in the period of analysis). The tables and figures presented in this paper show the 1948–2016 trends for the temperature indices and the 1948–2012 trends for the precipitation indices; the table and figures for the longer periods are provided in Tables S1 and S2 and Figs S1 to S4 (supplemental tables and figures can be accessed at <http://dx.doi.org/10.1080/07055900.2018.1514579>). The values of trend given in the text are all statistically significant.

d Regional and National Time Series

Canada is a vast country with many different climatic regions (Gullett & Skinner, 1992) and ecozones (Zhang et al., 2011). In this study, the country was divided into six broad regions

Fig. 2 The six regions (in red) used in this study: British Columbia region includes all stations in British Columbia (BC); Prairies region – all stations in Alberta (AB), Saskatchewan (SK) and Manitoba (MB); Ontario region – all stations in Ontario (ON); Quebec region – all stations in Quebec (QC); Atlantic region – all stations in New Brunswick (NB), Prince Edward Island (PE), Nova Scotia (NS), and Newfoundland and Labrador (NL-L); and Northern region – all stations in Yukon (YK), Northwest Territories (NT), and Nunavut (NU).

based on provincial boundaries (Fig. 2) to compare observed regional changes with those projected in the future. Because stations reporting climate observations are not evenly distributed in every region, with more stations in most populated areas, the following procedure was used to produce the regional and national time series. The country was first divided into 5° by 5° grid boxes. The anomalies (differences between the annual or seasonal values and their average over the reference period 1961–1990) were obtained at individual stations and were averaged within each grid box. The regional and national time series were then obtained by calculating the average of all boxes reporting within each region and the entire country. Because the annual highest 1-day rainfall, snowfall, and precipitation amounts can be very different from one station to another, the anomalies were further divided by the 1961–1990 average and multiplied by 100 to normalize the values for these indices. The trends for the temperature indices were computed for the 1948–2016 period for each region and Canada (the entire country) and for the 1900–2016 period for the southern regions and southern Canada (south of 60°N). The trends for the precipitation indices were computed similarly but for the 1948–2012 and 1900–2012 periods respectively.

3 Results

a Changes in Warm Conditions

Summer days (defined in Table 1) have significantly increased at most stations across the southern regions (Fig. 3a); this condition does not occur frequently in the north. The number of summer days averaged over the nation (south of 65°N) increased by 6.9 days during the 1948–2016 period (Table 3). The trends are significant in every southern region with the exception of the Prairies. During the 1900–2016 period (Table S1 and Fig. S1), the increase in summer days is more evident at stations in southern Ontario, southern Quebec, and the Maritime provinces (New Brunswick, Nova Scotia, and Prince Edward Island). The change in the number of summer days is not monotonic over the past 117 years: there is a small decreasing trend from the 1930s to the 1970s (Fig. 4a), probably because of the very hot daytime temperatures that occurred in the 1930s and 1940s in the Prairies (Bonsal et al., 2001).

Hot days are not commonly observed in regions north of 60°N or at locations on the Pacific and Atlantic coasts. Significant increasing trends of about 1–3 days are found at a handful of stations over the 1948–2016 period, mainly in southern British Columbia (BC), southern Quebec, and the Maritimes (Fig. 3a); decreasing trends are also observed in the Prairies. Similar results are noticed for the 1900–2016 period.

Hot nights are usually only observed in the southern areas of Manitoba, Ontario, and Quebec because other parts of Canada are not generally warm enough to experience nighttime temperatures above 22°C. In these areas, the number of hot nights has significantly increased at a few stations: by about 6 nights during the 1948–2016 period in Windsor and by 1–3 nights in London,

Fig. 3 Trends in warm and cold conditions during the 1948–2016 period. Filled triangles indicate trends significant at the 5% level. Black dots indicate that the condition does not frequently occur at the location (less than 5 years over the 1948–2016 period).

Hamilton, Toronto, and Montréal (Fig. 3a). During the past 117 years, the number of hot nights has significantly increased by about 1–3 nights in London, Toronto, and Montréal.

The summer 95th percentile of the daily maximum temperatures (tmax) and of the daily minimum temperatures (tmin) indicate significant increasing trends over the 1948–2016

period at many locations across the country (Fig. 5a, right panels); however, decreasing trends are also found in the summer 95th percentile of tmax, mainly in the Prairies. Averaged over the country, the summer 95th percentile of tmax has increased by 0.9°C for the 1948–2016 period, whereas the summer 95th percentile of tmin has increased by 1.3°C

TABLE 3. Regional trends for temperature indices for the 1948–2016 period.

Conditions	Indices	British Columbia	Prairies	Ontario	Quebec	Atlantic	Northern	Canada	Units
Warm	Summer days	5.8	6.7	11.4	6.0	10.7	n/a	6.9	days
	Hot days	3.3	0.8	2.0	0.9	1.7	n/a	n/a	days
	Hot nights	n/a	n/a	0.5	0.0	n/a	n/a	n/a	days
	Summer 95th perc. tmax	0.9	0.1	0.7	1.0	1.5	1.7	0.9	°C
	Summer 95th perc. tmin	1.5	1.0	1.1	1.8	1.9	1.8	1.3	°C
	Winter 95th perc. tmax	1.4	1.6	1.1	0.3	0.7	2.5	1.4	°C
Cold	Winter 95th perc. tmin	0.8	2.3	1.7	0.6	0.2	3.9	2.1	°C
	Frost days	-25.9	-10.4	-10.4	-16.7	-16.6	-16.3	-15.0	days
	Consecutive frost days	-18.6	-23.4	-22.2	-16.4	-8.3	-17.1	-18.6	days
	Ice days	-11.2	-17.5	-13.8	-13.5	-5.7	-12.1	-11.7	days
	Winter 5th perc. tmax	4.3	4.1	2.0	2.2	0.9	5.7	3.2	°C
	Winter 5th perc. tmin	5.1	4.5	2.6	2.2	1.9	5.4	3.5	°C
Frost-free season	Summer 5th perc. tmax	1.0	1.6	0.9	1.3	0.7	1.4	1.2	°C
	Summer 5th perc. tmin	1.7	1.3	1.4	1.5	1.1	1.8	1.4	°C
	Frost-free season (FFS)	31.2	15.0	13.5	25.5	19.9	24.2	20.1	days
Growing season	FFS starting date	-18.8	-6.8	-6.8	-9.7	-6.5	-8.5	-9.5	days
	FFS ending date	12.3	9.2	7.7	17.1	13.4	15.9	12.2	days
	Growing season (GS)	19.3	10.0	12.8	25.6	11.8	15.4	14.5	days
Degree-days	GS starting date	-12.6	-3.2	-6.6	-7.4	-5.3	-5.3	-6.4	days
	GS ending date	7.6	7.9	7.0	18.6	5.2	10.0	9.5	days
	Growing degree-days (GDD)	209.0	94.7	155.5	182.3	210.2	140.4	177.7	degree-days
Freeze–thaw days	Cooling degree-days (CDD)	34.0	21.6	60.4	31.6	52.1	n/a	32.1	degree-days
	Heating degree-days (HDD)	-298.7	-277.8	-270.1	-211.7	-204.9	-257.0	-159.8	degree-days
	Annual freeze–thaw days	-14.9	6.2	3.1	-7.6	-10.5	-5.8	-4.0	days
	Spring freeze–thaw days	-7.1	9.1	1.5	1.2	-0.5	3.0	1.6	days

Note: The numbers in bold indicate trends significant at the 5% level. The units are days, °C, or degree-days over the 1948–2016. “n/a” indicates not applicable.

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Fig. 4 Average anomalies of the number of (a) summer days and (b) frost days over Canada during the 1948–2016 period (blue) and southern Canada for the 1900–2016 period (red).

(Table 3). Therefore, very warm nighttime temperatures have increased more than very warm daytime temperatures during the summer. This is observed in every region although the trends in the summer very warm t_{max} are not significant in BC, the Prairies, and Ontario.

The winter 95th percentiles (warmest 5th percentile) for both t_{max} and t_{min} show significant increasing trends over the 1948–2016 period at most locations across the country (Fig. 5b, right panels). Averaged over the country, the winter 95th percentile of t_{max} has increased by 1.4°C for the 1948–2016 period, while the winter 95th percentile of t_{min} has increased by 2.1°C (Table 3). As seen during the summer, the trends are more pronounced in nighttime temperatures than in daytime temperatures; this is observed in every region with the exception of BC and the Atlantic region. In addition, the trends in the winter 95th daily temperature percentile (Fig. 5b, right panels) are generally more pronounced than those in the summer 95th percentile temperatures (Fig. 5a, right panels).

Similar results were found for the longer 1900–2016 period for southern Canada (Table S1 and Fig. S2); these include a larger increase in the 95th percentile of t_{min} than in the 95th percentile of t_{max} and stronger trends in the winter than in the summer. Winter temperatures appear to have greater inter-annual variability than summer temperatures (Fig. 6). The summer 95th percentile of t_{max} (Fig. 6a, top right panel) indicates a slight decrease from the 1930s to the 1970s, which can be attributed to the very hot daytime temperatures observed in the Prairies in the 1930s and 1940s (Bonsal et al., 2001).

b Changes in Cold Conditions

Cold conditions have become less cold across the country. The number of frost days has decreased at almost every station across the country and in the north (Fig. 3b). Averaged over the country, it has decreased by 15.0 days over the 1948–2016 period (Table 3). Regionally, the greatest reduction occurred in BC. The decrease during the 1900–2016 period is greater than the decrease during the 1948–2016 period in every region. Averaged over southern Canada, the number

of frost days has decreased by 22.9 days during the 1900–2016 period (Fig. 4b).

These results are consistent with the trends in other indices of cold conditions (Fig. 3b). Averaged over the country and for the 1948–2016 period, the number of consecutive frost days has decreased by 18.6 days while the number of ice days has decreased by 11.7 days (Table 3). Regionally, the largest decrease in the number of consecutive frost days and ice days over the past 69 years occurred in the Prairies. During the 1900–2016 period, the number of consecutive frost days has decreased by 26.7 days while the number of ice days has decreased by only 8.6 days (Table S1) probably because of the warm daytime temperatures observed in the 1930s and 1940s.

The winter 5th percentile of t_{max} and t_{min} has warmed more substantially than other similar indices (Fig. 5b, left panels). Averaged over the country, the winter 5th percentile of t_{max} has increased by 3.2°C for the 1948–2016 period, whereas the winter 5th percentile of t_{min} has increased by 3.5°C (Table 3). As seen before, the trends are more pronounced for nighttime temperatures than for daytime temperatures. Spatially, the warming is greater in the west and north: regionally, trends greater than 3°C are found in BC, the Prairies, and Northern region. The warming is more pronounced in the very cold winter temperatures (Fig 5b, left panels) than in the very warm winter temperatures (Fig. 5b, right panels), and the warming is greater in the winter (Fig. 5b) than the summer (Fig. 5a).

The summer 5th percentile of t_{max} , averaged over the country, has increased by 1.2°C for the 1948–2016 period, whereas the summer 5th percentile of t_{min} has increased by 1.4°C (Table 3). The change in the summer 5th percentiles of t_{max} and t_{min} (Fig. 5a) are consistent across the country, whereas those observed in the winter are more pronounced in western and northern regions (Fig. 5b).

The results are similar for the longer 1900–2016 period; the 5th percentile of t_{min} has increased more than the 5th percentile of t_{max} , and the trends are generally more pronounced in winter than summer. The warming is more pronounced in the very cold temperatures (5th percentile of t_{max} and t_{min})

Fig. 5 Trends in the 5th and 95th percentiles of the daily maximum and minimum temperatures during the 1948–2016 period for (a) summer and (b) winter ($^{\circ}\text{C}$ per 69 years). Filled triangles indicate trends significant at the 5% level. The largest triangles represent trends of about 4°C per 69 years.

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Fig. 6 5th and 95th percentiles of the daily maximum and minimum temperature anomalies averaged over Canada during the 1948–2016 period (blue) and southern Canada during the 1900–2016 period (red) for (a) summer and (b) winter.

during winter in southwestern regions (Fig. S2, left panels). Even if the time series for Canada (1948–2016) and southern Canada (1900–2016) show considerable interannual variability in the winter 5th percentiles compared with the winter 95th percentiles and to the summer 5th and 95th percentiles, statistically significant trends are still detectable in the winter very cold temperatures (Fig. 6).

c Changes in Frost-Free Season, Growing Season, Degree-Days, and Freeze-Thaw Days

The warming observed in winter mean temperatures has shortened the cold season in Canada. As a result, the frost-free season was extended by more than 20 days, on average, during the 1948–2016 period, starting earlier by about 9 days and ending later by about 12 days (Table 3). These

Fig. 7 Trends in (a) frost-free season, (b) growing season, (c) degree-days, and (d) freeze-thaw days during the 1948–2016 period. Filled triangles indicate trends significant at the 5% level. “DD” is used for degree-days. Black dots indicate that the condition does not occur frequently at the location (less than 5 years over the 1948–2016 period).

changes are seen at most stations across the country (Fig. 7a). Regionally, BC has had the greatest lengthening of the frost-free season. Over the longer 1900–2016 period, the trends are more pronounced in BC and the Prairies (Fig. S3). Averaged over southern Canada, the length of the frost-free season increased by about 25 days during the 1900–2016 period (Fig. 8a).

The length of the growing season averaged over Canada lengthened by about 15 days during the 1948–2016 period, starting 6 days earlier and ending 9 days later (Table 3). These changes are observed at most stations across the country (Fig. 7b); however, an earlier start to the growing season has not been observed at many locations in the Canadian Prairies, and the change in the starting date is not

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Fig. 8 (a) Frost-free season, (b) growing season, (c) degree-days, and (d) freeze-thaw day anomalies averaged over Canada during the 1948–2016 period (blue) and southern Canada during the 1900–2016 period (red).

significant in the Prairies (Table 3). The strongest changes in the growing season occurred in BC and Quebec during the 1948–2016 period (Table 3). Averaged over southern Canada, the length of the growing season also increased by about 15 days during the 1900–2016 period, and the increase is more pronounced from the 1970s to recent years (Fig. 8b).

The number of growing degree-days (GDD) has increased at most stations across the country (Fig. 7c) and the increase is significant in all regions for the 1948–2016 period (Table 3); for the longer 117-year period, significant

increasing trends are found in every region with the exception of the Prairies. The number of cooling degree-days (CDD) has increased at many stations located south of 55°N (Fig. 7c): over the 1900–2016 period, the trends are significant in every southern region. Conversely, the number of heating degree-days (HDD) has decreased at all stations across the country, including in the north (Fig. 7c), and the trends are significant in every region for the 1948–2016 and 1900–2016 periods. The time series for Canada and southern Canada show a gradual increase in the number of GDDs and CDDs

and a gradual decrease in HDDs with more interannual variability (Fig. 8c).

Changes in the annual and spring number of freeze–thaw days are not consistent across the country. The annual number of freeze–thaw days decreased at many locations in BC, southern Ontario, southern Quebec, the Maritimes, and the north during the 1948–2016 period; however, it has increased at most locations in the interior provinces (Fig. 7d). The number of spring freeze–thaw days follows a similar pattern of change across the country. Therefore, warming in central Canada has resulted in more days with daytime temperatures above zero while the nighttime temperatures remain below zero during the year and spring. Results are similar for the 1900–2016 period.

d *Changes in Wet Days*

The number of days with rainfall (≥ 1 mm) has increased in Canada. Although increasing trends are found at most locations across the country, they are more pronounced in the southern areas of BC and Ontario (Fig. 9a). The national series indicate that, on average, there has been an increase of 7.4 days with rainfall in Canada over the 1948–2012 period (Table 4). Regionally, the greatest increase occurred again in BC and Ontario. Averaged over southern Canada and for the 1900–2012 period, the number of days with rainfall has increased by about 8 days (Table S2). The time series for southern Canada shows a marked increase from the 1920s to the 1950s, followed by a smaller increase from the 1960s to 2012 (Fig. 10a).

Decreasing trends are found in the number of days with snowfall (≥ 1 mm) at most stations in the western provinces (BC to Manitoba) and at several stations in the east (from Ontario to the Maritimes); however, increasing trends are also found in the eastern regions and in the north (Fig. 9a). Regionally, BC has experienced a decrease of 6.3 days with snowfall for the 1948–2012 period, whereas the Northern region has seen an increase of 7.3 days (Table 4). During the 1900–2012 period, a positive trend is observed at most locations in the southern areas. The time series for southern Canada shows an increase from the 1900s to the mid-1970s, followed by a decrease to 2012 (Fig. 10a); the decreasing trend from the mid-1970s to 2012 is also evident over the shorter period for Canada as a whole.

The number of days with precipitation generally shows a mix of positive and negative trends, with some locations showing significant increasing trends (Fig. 9a). Regionally, the greatest increase occurs in the Northern region (Table 4). During the 1900–2012 period, the number of days with precipitation averaged over southern Canada has increased by 10.4 days (Table S2), and the increase is more pronounced from the 1900s to the 1950s (Fig. 10a).

e *Changes in Very Wet Days*

The number of days with heavy rainfall has increased by 2–3 days over the 1948–2012 period at several locations in BC,

southern Ontario, southern Quebec, and in the eastern provinces (Fig. 9b). The national average shows an increase of 1.3 days during the same period (Table 4). Regionally, the greatest increase occurs in the Atlantic region. During the 1900–2012 period, the number of days with heavy rainfall also increased by 2–3 days in BC and the Maritimes: the southern Canada series show a gradual increase of 1.6 days over the past 113 years (Fig. 10b).

Decreasing trends of about 2–3 days are found in the number of days with heavy snowfall at many locations in the western provinces and at a few locations in Ontario, Quebec, and the Maritimes; increasing trends are also observed at a few locations in the eastern regions and at several locations in the north (Fig. 9b). Regionally, BC experienced a decrease of 1.3 days over the 1948–2012 period, whereas the Northern region saw an increasing trend of 2.2 days (Table 4). The time series for southern Canada indicates a small increase from 1900 to the 1970s, followed by a decrease to 2012 (Fig. 10b).

The number of days with heavy precipitation generally shows a mix of positive and negative trends: however, several locations across the country show a significant increase of 3 days or more during the 1948–2012 period (Fig. 9b). Regionally, the greatest increase occurred in the Northern region (Table 4). The time series for southern Canada indicate a significant increase of 1.9 days with heavy precipitation over the past 113 years.

f *Changes in the Highest 1-Day Precipitation Events*

The annual highest 1-day rainfall, snowfall, and precipitation amounts have not changed considerably at most locations during either the 1948–2012 or 1900–2012 periods; a significant increasing trend was found at only a handful of stations (Fig. 9c). None of the regions indicate a significant change during the 1948–2012 or 1900–2012 periods. The time series for southern Canada shows an increasing (but not significant) trend in the annual highest 1-day rainfall and 1-day precipitation, whereas the time series for the annual 1-day snowfall shows a small increase from the beginning of the period to the 1970s followed by a decrease to 2012 (Fig. 10c); this time series also has considerable interannual variability.

g *Changes in Dry Conditions*

The maximum number of consecutive dry days (MCDD) shows a mix of positive and negative trends across the country (Fig. 9d). This index significantly decreased by 6–9 days at several locations in the southwest regions during the 1948–2012 period. Averaged over the country, the MCDD has not changed significantly during the past 65 years (Table 4). During the 1900–2012 period, the MCDD decreased at most locations in BC and the Prairies (Fig. S4). Averaged over southern Canada, the MCDD has decreased by about 6 days over the past 113 years: the time series shows a

Trends in Indices Based on Daily Temperature and Precipitation Data / 13

Fig. 9 Trends in precipitation indices during the 1948–2012 period. Filled triangles indicate trends significant at the 5% level.

decreasing trend which is more pronounced from 1900 to the 1960s (Fig. 10d).

4 Discussion

Changes in Canada’s climate are evident. The indices examined in this study were chosen to provide insights into current and potential future impacts of ongoing climate change on Canadians and sectors of the Canadian economy.

a Health

Hot days have increased by 1–3 days at a handful of stations in southern BC, Quebec, and the Maritimes. Hot nights have increased by 1–3 nights at a few stations in southern Ontario and Quebec. The summer 95th percentile of tmax and tmin, averaged over the country, has increased by 0.9° and 1.3°C, respectively, for the 1948–2016 period, and increasing trends were found across the nation. These very warm temperature conditions have the potential to have serious effects on human health and well-being in Canada (Berry, Clarke,

TABLE 4. Regional trends for precipitation indices for the 1948–2012 period.

Conditions	Indices	British Columbia	Prairies	Ontario	Quebec	Atlantic	Northern	Canada	Units
Wet	Days with rainfall	11.3	4.1	8.0	4.8	0.2	3.1	7.4	days
	Days with snowfall	-6.3	-2.7	-0.2	-3.7	-4.7	7.3	-1.6	days
	Days with precipitation	4.6	-0.7	5.7	0.7	-3.4	9.6	3.4	days
Very wet	Days with heavy rainfall	0.7	0.2	1.3	2.1	2.6	0.7	1.3	days
	Days with heavy snowfall	-1.3	-0.7	-0.2	-0.3	0.0	2.2	-0.4	days
	Days with heavy precipitation	0.1	-0.2	1.9	1.9	1.9	2.6	1.1	days
Highest	Highest 1-day rainfall	2.6	-3.3	3.6	8.0	6.8	8.0	4.1	%
	Highest 1-day snowfall	-12.0	-11.3	-4.1	8.1	2.6	9.1	-7.6	%
	Highest 1-day precipitation	-0.2	-3.2	2.5	8.1	8.4	7.0	3.0	%
Dry	Maximum number of consecutive dry days (MCDD)	-1.8	-0.1	-0.4	0.3	-0.5	-0.6	-0.8	days

Note: The numbers in bold indicate trends significant at the 5% level. The units are days or % over the 1948–2012 period.

Fleury, & Parker, 2014), and their occurrence is expected to increase as the climate continues to warm in these regions (Casati et al., 2013).

b Tourism

Summer days have increased at most stations south of 65°N: the national average indicates an increase of 6.9 more summer days during the 1948–2016 period. This change in warm conditions can be beneficial for summer tourism activities including golfing, fishing, canoeing, and camping because these activities will profit from a longer warm-weather season (Kovacs & Thistlethwaite, 2014). Conversely, days with snowfall and heavy snowfall have decreased by 2–3 days at many locations in the western provinces and at a few locations in Ontario, Quebec, and the Maritimes. As temperature continues to increase and days with snowfall and heavy snowfall continue to decrease, tourism based on winter sports, such as skiing and snowmobiling, will suffer from warmer temperatures and less snow on the ground (Kovacs & Thistlethwaite, 2014).

c Agriculture

The growing season has become longer by an average of more than 15 days over Canada during the past 69 years and an increase in GDDs has been observed at most stations across the country. Longer and warmer growing seasons would allow crops to be grown farther north, where soil conditions permit, and lengthen outdoor feeding seasons for livestock (Campbell, Durant, Hunter, & Hyatt, 2014). However, there will be new pests and diseases, as well as other challenges that could negatively affect agricultural sectors (Campbell et al., 2014). Fewer days with snowfall and heavy snowfall resulting in less snow on the ground during the spring could also have a negative impact on agriculture as water availability decreases (Blankinship & Hart, 2012).

d Energy Consumption

The winter 5th percentiles of tmax and of tmin, averaged over the country, have increased by 3.2° and 3.5°C, respectively, during the 1948–2016 period, and HDDs have substantially decreased at all stations. This reduction in HDDs along with fewer very cold days and frost days could reduce the demand for heating buildings and energy consumption

(Instanes, 2005). However, many stations located south of 55°N have indicated an increase in CDDs, which can also affect the demand for energy (Instanes, 2005).

e Shipping Industry

Fewer frost days and consecutive frost days have been observed at almost all stations across the country. The number of frost days and consecutive frost days, averaged over the nation, decreased by more than 15 and 18 days, respectively, during the 1948–2016 period, resulting in a longer frost-free season by more than 20 days. A longer frost-free season can affect the shipping industry because ships will be able to travel on the Great Lakes and St. Lawrence Seaway for a longer period of time if water levels permit (Andrey et al., 2014). In addition, the shipping season in the Arctic will become longer assuming favourable ice conditions (Weller, 2005).

f Road Maintenance and Production of Maple Syrup

The annual and spring number of freeze–thaw days decreased at many locations in BC, southern Ontario, southern Quebec, and in the Maritimes during the 1948–2016 period, whereas it has increased in the interior provinces. The warming in central Canada has resulted in more days with daytime temperatures above zero, while nighttime temperatures remain below zero. This change in weather conditions can have a negative impact on road maintenance (Hershfield, 1979; Ho & Gough, 2006; Schmidlin et al., 1987). Fewer freeze–thaw days during the spring can negatively influence the production of maple syrup in the southern regions of Ontario and Quebec (Duchesne et al., 2009; Pothier, 1995).

5 Conclusions

This study presents observed trends in several indices relevant to climate change impacts based on daily temperature and precipitation data. The indices are computed using the latest version of the daily homogenized temperature and adjusted precipitation, and the analyses presented here update some previous work by examining trends over a longer period of time. The number of stations with temperature and precipitation observations decreased considerably after 2005, mainly as a

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Fig. 10 Anomalies in precipitation indices averaged over Canada during the 1948–2012 period (blue) and southern Canada during the 1900–2012 period (red).

result of relocation and closure of traditional manual observation stations and the introduction of automated systems. Work is in progress for joining past manual and current automated weather observations in order to preserve continuity for climate trends and monitoring (Milewska et al., 2018; Milewska & Hogg, 2002; Milewska & Vincent, 2016; Vincent, Milewska, Wang, & Hartwell, 2018).

Results regarding the changes in very warm and very cold temperatures (defined by the summer and winter 95th and 5th percentiles of t_{max} and t_{min}) have revealed three important

pieces of information. First, very cold temperatures have increased more than very warm temperatures. This is evident in stronger warming trends at the lower end of the daily temperature distribution than at the higher end (the 5th percentile has increased more than the 95th percentile). Second, nighttime very warm and very cold temperatures have warmed more than daytime very warm and very cold temperatures, both in the cold and warm seasons. This result is consistent with greater warming observed at nighttime than during daytime (Vincent et al., 2012). Finally, the trends are more pronounced

during winter than during summer. Overall, these results are consistent with earlier publications (Bonsal et al., 2001; Wang et al., 2014) that have shown fewer days with low temperatures and more days with high temperatures, which together depict Canada's climate as becoming not only warmer but also much less cold. These results are also in agreement with those of the *Fifth Assessment Report* from the Intergovernmental Panel on Climate Change, which states that this kind of response should be expected in a warmer world (Collins et al., 2013; Kirtman et al., 2013). Explaining the causes of the diurnal asymmetry in Canada's warming is beyond the scope of the paper; however, a recent study has suggested that the diurnal asymmetry in observed global warming could be a result of shallow boundary layers forming at night (Davy, Esau, Chernokulsky, Outten, & Zilitinkevich, 2017).

The changes in precipitation indices show considerable spatial and temporal variability, and the trends at regional and national scales are based on a limited number of stations. Overall, the number of days with rainfall and heavy rainfall has increased in the southern regions, while the number of days with snowfall and heavy snowfall has decreased in the western regions and increased in the north during the past 65 years. It is possible that at a number of stations in the south, the precipitation type changed from solid to liquid around the 1970s because of warmer spring temperatures resulting in fewer days with snowfall and heavy snowfall in the southern regions. The number of days with precipitation and with heavy precipitation has increased at several stations across the country. While significant increasing trends in the annual highest 1-day rainfall, 1-day snowfall, and 1-day precipitation can be found at some isolated stations, the spatial distribution of these stations does not form a spatial clustering pattern and the percentage of stations showing significant trends is not larger than would be expected by chance. It is concluded that there is no evidence of significant change in this type of extreme precipitation for Canada as a whole. The lack of a detectable significant change in extreme precipitation for the country means that changes in extreme precipitation, if they exist, may still be too small to be distinguishable from natural climatic variability. These findings are also in agreement with the trends observed in short-duration (a day or shorter) extreme rainfall amounts (Mekis, Vincent, Shephard, & Zhang, 2015; Shephard et al., 2014).

Most of the findings regarding trends in indices based on daily temperature and precipitation reported in previous studies are supported by the current analysis that included more recent years and used the best available data for trend analysis. The consistency of these results indicates that the detected trends are robust and are not caused by non-climatic factors, such as relocation of observing sites and changes in observing procedures. However, some of the results are different. This includes the trends in winter 5th and 95th percentiles of tmax and tmin in the northeast region of the country which show an increase over the 1948–2016 period and a decrease

over the 1950–1998 period (Bonsal et al., 2001). An additional 17 years of recent data have reversed the trends from negative to positive at most stations in this region. This suggests the importance of low-frequency modes of climate variability, such as the North Atlantic Oscillation (Yu, Lin, Wu, & Merryfield, 2017), affecting the long-term climate trend. Another important difference is the trend in the number of days with rainfall. Averaged over the country, the current study has found an increase of about 7 days over the 1948–2012 period, whereas Vincent and Mekis (2006) show a much larger increase, of about 20 days, for the 1950–2003 period. The difference is largely due to a difference in the definition of a day with rainfall. In Vincent and Mekis (2006), days with rainfall greater than the trace amount were first used. It was then recognized that the trace events have not been reported consistently in the past, leading to potential inhomogeneities in the annual number of days with rainfall. In the current study, days with rainfall greater than or equal to 1 mm were used instead to avoid these inhomogeneities. Despite the different definitions and possible inhomogeneities in Vincent and Mekis (2006), the conclusion of an increase in the number of days with rainfall is robust.

In conclusion, this study improves our knowledge of trends in climate conditions affecting Canadians. The results are consistent with expectations based on a warming climate, and Canada has already warmed substantially over the past century. The lack of increasing trends in summer very warm temperature in the Prairies and no consistently observed changes in the annual highest 1-day precipitation amount for the country as a whole are noted, but a warming climate does not necessarily mean that all regions will warm at the same rate and that precipitation will change similarly. Further research is needed to understand the causes of changes at regional levels because these indices demonstrate a high degree of spatial variability. Further research is also needed to better understand how changes in daily temperature and precipitation conditions can affect Canada's economy and ecological systems, as well as the everyday lives of Canadians.

Acknowledgements

The authors would like to thank Sharon Stone and Robert Whitewood from Environment and Climate Change Canada and two anonymous reviewers for their useful comments and suggestions that helped improve the manuscript.

Disclosure statement

No potential conflict of interest was reported by the authors.

Supplemental Data

Supplemental information for this article can be accessed at <http://dx.doi.org/10.1080/07055900.2018.1514579>.

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Hartwell,Megan (ECCC)

From: Vincent, Lucie (ECCC)
Sent: June 17, 2021 12:32 PM
To: Joseph Hickey
Subject: RE: Question re: extending AHCCD precipitation data beyond 2011 for several cities

Hi Joseph,

The metadata is not in a user-friendly format and it is not distributed.

All the best with your work!

Lucie

From: Joseph Hickey <JHickey@bank-banque-canada.ca>
Sent: June 16, 2021 12:05 PM
To: Vincent, Lucie (EC) <lucie.vincent@canada.ca>
Subject: RE: Question re: extending AHCCD precipitation data beyond 2011 for several cities

Category/Catégorie: Non-Sensitive/Non-Délicat

Hi Lucie,

Thanks a lot for this helpful information.

Another question – journal articles often refer to “metadata” for Canadian weather stations (information about when a station moved or instruments changed, etc.). Do you know how I could access this metadata? Is it available online somewhere?

Thanks,
Joseph

From: Vincent, Lucie (EC) <lucie.vincent@canada.ca>
Sent: June 4, 2021 10:57 AM
To: Joseph Hickey <JHickey@bank-banque-canada.ca>
Subject: {External} RE: Question re: extending AHCCD precipitation data beyond 2011 for several cities

CAUTION: This email comes from outside the Bank. Please exercise caution with external content and attachments. Contact Security if you have any concerns.

ATTENTION: Ce courriel provient d'une source extérieure. Prenez des précautions quand vous recevez des courriels qui ont du contenu externe et des pièces jointes. Si vous avez la moindre inquiétude, communiquez avec la Sécurité.

Hi Joseph,

s.19(1)

I am sorry to not have replied to your message earlier.

During the past 20 years, the number of climatological stations in Canada, which report manned-made precipitation observations, has decreased very much. Today most of the precipitation measurements are made by an automatic

system. Researchers in Environment Canada are developing methodologies to merge past manned observations with current automated observations to create long and continuous records of precipitation. This takes lots of time.

The precipitation from the AHCCD and ADRSD are mainly manned precipitation observations. For example, the period of data for the station 3031093 Calgary Int'l A is 1881-2012 for both datasets. I don't think that it will be possible to merge AHCCD to ADRSD observations with same stnid to create a long record. If you join observations from two different stnids then it is likely that you will create an artificial shift at the joining date.

The stations list is provided at the ADRSD website (here attached). Good luck with your work.

Lucie

From: Joseph Hickey <JHickey@bank-banque-canada.ca>
Sent: May 25, 2021 5:38 PM
To: Vincent, Lucie (EC) <lucie.vincent@canada.ca>
Cc: Tatjana Dahlhaus <tdahlhaus@bank-banque-canada.ca>
Subject: RE: Question re: extending AHCCD precipitation data beyond 2011 for several cities

Category/Catégorie: Non-Sensitive/Non-Délicat

Hi Dr. Vincent,

Just wanted to follow up on this,

Cheers,
Joseph

From: Joseph Hickey
Sent: May 11, 2021 10:59 AM
To: 'lucie.vincent@canada.ca' <lucie.vincent@canada.ca>
Cc: Tatjana Dahlhaus <tdahlhaus@bank-banque-canada.ca>
Subject: Question re: extending AHCCD precipitation data beyond 2011 for several cities

Category/Catégorie: Non-Sensitive/Non-Délicat

Dear Dr. Vincent,

I'm working on a project at the Bank of Canada regarding effects of weather events on economic indicators such as employment. (I believe you previously were in contact with Julien McDonald-Guimond about a related project using temperature data that was also done in my department at the Bank.)

In our current project, we are using Environment and Climate Change Canada's Adjusted and Homogenized Canadian Climate Data (AHCCD), and are focusing on stations for a set of Canadian cities. As a first step in this project, we'd like to examine how several precipitation indices have changed over the time period from 1961 to present.

We've found that the precipitation component of the AHCCD (the 2nd Generation Daily Adjusted Precipitation for Canada – Update to December 2017) only contains data up to the end of 2011 for many of our cities. However, in the [Word document](#) describing the 2nd Gen. Precip. dataset, there is a note at the top (in red font) referring to the "[Adjusted Daily Rainfall and Snowfall Dataset](#)" (ADRSD).

I'm wondering if it is possible to extend the AHCCD precipitation data beyond 2011 for our cities, using the ADRSD? I.e., can one simply append the ADRSD data for 2011-forward onto the AHCCD data up-to-2011, or would doing so introduce artifacts into the time-series due to issues such as stations being in different locations, etc.?

(I assume that simply appending the ADRSD to the AHCCD for the station associated with a particular city in the AHCCD would introduce such artifacts, since creating the AHCCD involved homogenization procedures to join different stations together, and my understanding from reading the ECC documentation is that this has not been done for the ADRSD stations. However, I would like to confirm if this is correct?)

For example, the precipitation station for Calgary (id 3031093) in the AHCCD only has data up to the end of 2011. If we were to append the ADRSD data for a "Calgary" station in the ADRSD to the data for precipitation station 3031093 from the AHCCD, would this introduce an artifact?

Also, could you point me to a list of stations included in the ADRSD? (I wasn't able to find one at the [website](#) for the ADRSD.)

For your info, our cities of interest are the Census Metropolitan Areas that have both temperature and precipitation stations associated with them in the AHCCD, namely: Belleville, Calgary, Edmonton, Halifax, Hamilton, Kelowna, Kingston, Lethbridge, London, Moncton, Montreal, Ottawa, Peterborough, Regina, Saint John, Saskatoon, St. John's, Sudbury, Toronto, Vancouver, Victoria, Windsor, and Winnipeg.

Thank you for any guidance you can provide on these questions,

Best,
Joseph

--

Joseph Hickey, Ph.D.

Data Scientist | Scientifique des données

Canadian Economic Analysis | Analyses de l'économie canadienne

Bank of Canada | Banque du Canada

234 rue Wellington Street, Ottawa ON K1A 0G9

Telephone | Téléphone : 613-782-7257

jhickey@bank-banque-canada.ca

Hartwell, Megan (ECCC)

From: Julien McDonald-Guimond <JMcDonald-Guimond@bank-banque-canada.ca>
Sent: February 16, 2021 3:50 PM
To: Hartwell, Megan (EC)
Subject: RE: AHCCD Temperature Update 3rd Gen

Category/Catégorie: Non-Sensitive/Non-Délicat

Hi Megan,

Thank you very much for this update. I'm glad to see that my input could be useful and am looking forward to using the new dataset! On a side note, I wish to let you know that the spreadsheet you've compiled where one can see the different stations used to construct the final AHCCD station is a great addition.

All the best,
Julien

Julien Mc Donald-Guimond

Économiste | Economist
Section des études sur l'économie canadienne | Canadian Economic Studies Division
Analyse de l'économie canadienne | Canadian Economic Analysis

234 rue Wellington Street, Ottawa ON K1A 0G9
JMcDonald-Guimond@bank-banque-canada.ca

De : Hartwell, Megan (EC) <megan.hartwell@canada.ca>
Envoyé : 15 février 2021 3:51
À : Julien McDonald-Guimond <JMcDonald-Guimond@bank-banque-canada.ca>
Objet : {External} AHCCD Temperature Update 3rd Gen

Hello Julien,

I'm happy to inform you that the third generation of homogenized temperature has now been updated to include 2020 data (http://crd-data-donnees-rdc.ec.gc.ca/CDAS/products/AHCCD_daily/)

A few improvements were made to the previous version, one of which you highlighted for us.

The days where tmax and tmin were reversed were fixed. There are several steps to this. If the data begins with this issue (the official archive version has tx < tn), the values are either manually corrected (typically missing a negative sign or decimal place) so moved to the average of the two values, plus or minus 0.1. The values then undergo the adjustments described in the paper. After all these adjustments were made the values were again checked for tx < tn. If problematic, the adjusted value was then corrected to respect the tmax and tmin relationship.

A number of missing mean values were estimated when either tmax or tmin were available. These values were estimated when the opposing element was available, using the dates on either side of the missing day of the same element.

Thank you again for choosing this dataset to work with and please let me know if you require anything further.

Megan Hartwell

Climate Data Analyst, Climate Research Division
Environment and Climate Change Canada / Government of Canada
megan.hartwell@canada.ca / Tel.: 416-739-4349

Analyste de données climatologiques, Recherche climatique
Environnement et Changement climatique Canada / Gouvernement du Canada
megan.hartwell@canada.ca / Tél.: 416-739-4349

A second generation of homogenized Canadian monthly surface air temperature for climate trend analysis

Lucie A. Vincent,¹ Xiaolan L. Wang,¹ Ewa J. Milewska,¹ Hui Wan,¹ Feng Yang,¹ and Val Swail¹

Received 28 March 2012; revised 8 August 2012; accepted 9 August 2012; published 22 September 2012.

[1] This study presents a second generation of homogenized monthly mean surface air temperature data set for Canadian climate trend analysis. Monthly means of daily maximum and of daily minimum temperatures were examined at 338 Canadian locations. Data from co-located observing sites were sometimes combined to create longer time series for use in trend analysis. Time series of observations were then adjusted to account for nation-wide change in observing time in July 1961, affecting daily minimum temperatures recorded at 120 synoptic stations; these were adjusted using hourly temperatures at the same sites. Next, homogeneity testing was performed to detect and adjust for other discontinuities. Two techniques were used to detect non-climatic shifts in de-seasonalized monthly mean temperatures: a multiple linear regression based test and a penalized maximal t test. These discontinuities were adjusted using a recently developed quantile-matching algorithm: the adjustments were estimated with the use of a reference series. Based on this new homogenized temperature data set, annual and seasonal temperature trends were estimated for Canada for 1950–2010 and Southern Canada for 1900–2010. Overall, temperature has increased at most locations. For 1950–2010, the annual mean temperature averaged over the country shows a positive trend of 1.5°C for the past 61 years. This warming is slightly more pronounced in the minimum temperature than in the maximum temperature; seasonally, the greatest warming occurs in winter and spring. The results are similar for Southern Canada although the warming is considerably greater in the minimum temperature compared to the maximum temperature over the period 1900–2010.

Citation: Vincent, L. A., X. L. Wang, E. J. Milewska, H. Wan, F. Yang, and V. Swail (2012), A second generation of homogenized Canadian monthly surface air temperature for climate trend analysis, *J. Geophys. Res.*, *117*, D18110, doi:10.1029/2012JD017859.

1. Introduction

[2] The development of high-quality surface air temperature data sets has received considerable attention in recent years due to the rising interest in understanding and quantifying how our climate is changing. Long-term time series of reliable temperature data at fine time and spatial resolution are required for a better assessment of climate variability and change on local and regional scale, as well as changes in extremes. High-quality temperatures data are also needed in near real-time to monitor the effects of climate change and extreme events on today's society.

[3] Original temperature records are not always suitable for proper analysis of climate change. Non-climatic variations

(inhomogeneities) are often present in temperature series due to changes in instrumentation, in local site condition and environment, in observing practices and observing time, as well as site relocation and station automation, etc. (these are among the main factors leading to inhomogeneities in temperature records [Trewin, 2010]). Inhomogeneities can seriously interfere with the proper assessment of any climate trends and extremes. For this reason, testing and adjusting (if necessary) temperature time series have become an essential component of climate analysis.

[4] A large number of techniques have been developed for detection of inhomogeneities in temperature series: see Venema *et al.* [2012], Aguilar *et al.* [2003] and Peterson *et al.* [1998] for detailed reviews. Many of these techniques were applied to original temperature data time series in order to homogenize them. Trend analysis using homogenized temperatures was carried out in Australia [Della-Marta *et al.*, 2004], China [Li *et al.*, 2009], Finland and the North Atlantic countries [Tuomenvirta, 2001], Switzerland [Begert *et al.*, 2005], Spain [Brunet *et al.*, 2006], the United States [Menne *et al.*, 2009], and Canada [Vincent and Gullett, 1999], to name a few. Many homogenized data sets were also included

¹Climate Research Division, Science and Technology Branch, Environment Canada, Toronto, Ontario, Canada.

Corresponding author: L. A. Vincent, Climate Research Division, Science and Technology Branch, Environment Canada, 4905 Dufferin St., Toronto, ONT M3H 5T4, Canada. (lucie.vincent@ec.gc.ca)

Published in 2012 by the American Geophysical Union.

in the global temperature data sets to obtain an estimate of temperature averages at global scale [Jones *et al.*, 2012]. A few studies have compared the ability of various techniques for detecting inhomogeneities in temperature series [Ducré-Robitaille *et al.*, 2003; DeGaetano, 2006; Reeves *et al.*, 2007; Domonkos, 2011]. The large number of different techniques and the need for a realistic comparative study has led to a coordinated European initiative, the COST Action Advances in Homogenization Methods of Climate Series [Venema *et al.*, 2012; Action COST ES0601, 2011]. Most techniques were developed to homogenize annual and monthly mean temperatures in order to produce long-term homogeneous series to improve estimates of trends and variability.

[5] In the mid-1990s, a first generation of homogenized temperature data sets was prepared for the analysis of climate trends in Canada [Vincent and Gullett, 1999]. Non-climatic shifts due to station relocation and change in observing time were identified in the annual means of daily maximum and minimum temperatures using a technique based on regression models and neighboring stations [Vincent, 1998]. Monthly adjustments were obtained from fitting regression models to monthly mean data series for each calendar month separately and applied to bring each homogeneous segment into agreement with the most recent homogeneous part of the series. For each non-climatic shift, the 12 monthly adjustments were later interpolated to each calendar day to derive daily adjustments, which were applied to produce the first generation of homogenized daily maximum and minimum temperatures [Vincent *et al.*, 2002]. Homogenized data sets were prepared for 210 locations across the country. Co-located station observations were sometimes joined in time to produce a longer time series. These homogenized temperatures were used in many studies including the analysis of trends in annual and seasonal temperature and precipitation in Canada [Zhang *et al.*, 2000], changes in temperature and precipitation daily indices [Vincent and Mekis, 2006], hemispheric and global assessment of temperature averages [Jones and Moberg, 2003], and global assessment of extreme temperature and precipitation changes [Alexander *et al.*, 2006].

[6] In this study, a second generation of homogenized monthly mean temperature data sets is developed with a number of improvements. First, the station list was revised to include more stations, offering a better spatial and temporal coverage. Second, a new adjustment method was applied to the daily minimum temperatures of 120 stations in order to resolve the bias caused by the change in observing time in 1961. Third, although the first generation of homogenized temperature data sets were updated every year with the most current data, homogeneity testing and adjustments have been done thoroughly only twice, in mid-1990s and early 2000s. Therefore, there was an urgent need to re-test the full period at each station and to adjust the data accordingly if necessary; in this study, a couple of techniques for detecting non-climatic shifts were used in an attempt to obtain the best possible results. Finally, a newly developed quantile-matching (QM) adjustment algorithm was applied to adjust for the identified non-climatic shifts in monthly mean temperature series.

[7] The primary objective of this study is to document all procedures used to produce the second generation of homogenized monthly mean temperature data sets. Proper documentation is crucial for assisting users to comprehend

any limitations of the data sets and to ensure a proper interpretation of the results derived from the data sets. A second objective is to present an updated analysis of the annual and seasonal temperature trends in Canada using the newly homogenized data sets which cover a longer period of time (to 2010) and have an improved spatial coverage.

[8] The rest of this paper is organized as follows. Section 2 describes the data and methodologies, and in particular joining of observations from co-located stations, adjustments of daily minimum temperatures for the change in observing time in 1961, detection and adjustment of non-climatic shifts in monthly data series. Section 3 presents the estimated trends in annual and seasonal means of the daily maximum, minimum and mean temperatures for Canada for 1950–2010 and Southern Canada for 1900–2010. A discussion is provided in section 4 and a few concluding remarks are given in section 5.

2. Data and Methodologies

2.1. Data

[9] Daily maximum and minimum temperatures were directly retrieved from the National Climate Data Archive of Environment Canada. The station selection was based on data quality, longevity, spatial and temporal coverage, including counts of missing values. Homogenized data sets were produced for 338 locations (Figure 1). Most of these stations are the same as those in the first generation, except that 10 stations had to be removed due to their proximity to other selected sites or count of missing values. Some viable stations from the second generation of adjusted precipitation data set [Mekis and Vincent, 2011] were included in this new version to provide both daily temperature and precipitation at as many common locations as possible. Figure 1 shows that the newly added stations improve spatial coverage, mainly in the south (only nine stations were added north of 60°N). Temporal coverage is also improved since many of the added stations have long records in the past (Figure 1). The main goal of the first generation data set was to analyze the trends for the century 1895–1995. In the second generation, the entire record of each station is used, including 19 stations with data starting in the 1870s and one station (Toronto) with daily temperatures from 1840 to the present.

2.2. Joining of Co-located Stations Observations

[10] The climate observing network in Canada has considerably changed over its long period of taking climate observations, especially since 1990 due to the downsizing of the traditional network and the increased use of automated systems. For this reason, station closures and relocations are two major and ongoing issues in Canada. A new station identification number is often given to the new station when it opens or is relocated (station relocations can also occur without a change in identification number). In order to have long time series useful for trends analysis, it was often necessary to merge observations at co-located stations, which were usually no more than 20 km apart. This was done for 63% of the stations (213 locations) in the second generation data sets. Sometimes, the observations of three or four stations were joined to form a long series. Overall, 43% of the stations have one joining date, and 16% and 4% of the stations have two and three joining dates, respectively.

Figure 1. Location of the second generation's 338 stations (circles) and first generation's 210 stations (dots). Number of stations in the second generation (gray) and first generation (black) reporting per year.

[11] Figure 2 shows the number of joining dates per year. A first peak is observed in 1942/1943: these joining dates generally correspond to rural observing sites (located at houses or farms) that were closed while the instruments were relocated to nearby newly built airport stations. The second peak in 1965/1966 does not have any particular documented cause. The third peak around 1994/1995/1996 is largely due to stations that have fully or partially ceased human observations: these sites were often closed and then re-opened with automated observing systems. The last peaks of 2005 and 2008 are not necessarily associated with station closures but mainly to the introduction of a new practice regarding the quality assurance/control (QA/QC) applied to daily climate data. To ensure continuity of daily temperature time series in the recent years, for the second generation data sets, it was sometimes necessary to merge data that have received a complete set of routine QA/QC procedures in the past with newer data that have received minimal or no QC in the archives. Because of this, for the purpose of this study, a few basic checks had to be applied to ensure that the data extracted from the archives was reasonable. Daily temperatures below -60°C and above 50°C were identified and compared to neighbors: data value was retained or set to missing. Long sequences of consecutive zero values at a few automatic sites were as well identified and set to missing.

2.3. Correction of the Bias in Daily Minimum Temperatures Caused by the Change in Observing Time in 1961

[12] During the preparation of the first generation of homogenized temperature data sets [Vincent and Gullett, 1999], a decreasing shift in 1961 of about 0.6 to 0.8°C on average was identified in the annual mean of the daily minimum temperatures at many synoptic stations (mainly airports). This "bias" was found to have resulted from a nation-wide change in observing time on 1 July 1961 at synoptic stations. In 1961, it was decided to change the

reporting time of the daily minimum temperature from the 24-h observing window ending at 0000 UTC (coordinated universal time) to the window ending at 0600 UTC. Since the 0600 UTC hour corresponds more closely to the time when the actual daily minimum temperature occurs, particularly in eastern Canada, it was more likely that the same minimum (or a similar minimum) temperature was recorded on two successive calendar days, consequently introducing a cold bias in the annual and monthly means of daily minimum temperatures. For maximum temperature, the observing window was changed from 1200 UTC to 0600 UTC in July 1961: the effect of this change on daily maximum temperature was considered to be negligible [Vincent *et al.*, 2009; Cameron and Wilson, 1996]. In a separate study involving many observing stations across Canada, Hopkinson *et al.* [2011] quantified that this change for maximum temperature affected much fewer stations than in the case of minimum temperature and the magnitude of the difference between observing windows was also much smaller.

Figure 2. Number of joining dates per year (for the second generation data set).

Figure 3. Annual mean of the daily minimum temperatures for Greenwood, Nova Scotia, before (gray – dashed line) and after (black – solid line) adjustments for observation time change in 1961.

[13] During the preparation of the first generation data set, the adjustments were performed in the following way. Since the most recent period (since 1961) was affected, monthly adjustments derived from regression models were applied to bring the monthly data for the period since 1961 into agreement with the second most recent homogeneous part of the series (before 1961). Later, adjustments were also applied to all daily values by interpolating the monthly adjustments to each calendar day of year [Vincent *et al.*, 2002]. At that time, these adjustments were considered to be sufficient for the purpose of preserving consistency between adjusted daily data and homogeneous monthly data time series, while further investigation of this bias was deemed necessary.

[14] Recently, the cold bias in the minimum temperatures was further investigated by Vincent *et al.* [2009]. They found that not all days were affected by the change in observing window in 1961: the annual percentage of affected days ranged from 15% for locations in the west to 38% for locations in the east. Further, they developed a procedure that uses hourly temperature observations to adjust daily minimum temperatures. This procedure includes the following steps. First, an affected day is detected when the lowest hourly temperature in the 24-h window ending at 0600 UTC is colder than the lowest hourly temperature in the 24-h window ending at 0000 UTC. Then, for this particular day, the daily minimum is estimated to be 0.5°C lower than the lowest hourly temperature in the 24-h window ending at 0000 UTC (the subtraction of 0.5°C is to remove the small difference between the true daily minimum and the lowest hourly temperature; see Vincent *et al.* [2009] for more details).

[15] In the current study, the approach developed by Vincent *et al.* [2009] was applied to correct the cold bias in daily minimum temperatures recorded at 120 synoptic stations over the period since 1961. Adjusting the period prior 1961 (instead of after 1961) would have resolved the decreasing step detected in the monthly time series, but it would also have created “incorrect” daily minimum temperatures before 1961 that do not correspond to actual minimums in the daily temperature cycle. In addition, adjusting minimum temperatures after 1961 has preserved consistency between synoptic and volunteer stations [Hopkinson *et al.*, 2011]. An example of the impact of this correction on annual values is provided

for the station Greenwood, Nova Scotia. As shown in Figure 3, the time series shows warmer annual temperatures after the correction, which consequently affects the overall trend. In the future, when updating the second generation data sets, the same procedure will be applied to correct daily minimum temperatures of the most current year.

2.4. Detection of Non-climatic Shifts in Monthly Series

[16] In this study, two techniques were applied to detect non-climatic shifts in monthly mean temperature time series: the multiple linear regressions (MLR) based test [Vincent, 1998] that was used for the first generation of homogenized temperatures, and a penalized maximal t (PMT) test based algorithm [Wang *et al.*, 2007; Wang, 2008]. Other studies have also used multiple tests for detection of non-climatic shifts in temperature time series [Menne and Williams, 2005; Wijngaard *et al.*, 2003]. Although inhomogeneities may take the form of change in mean or in variance, or in both, the focus here is to detect changes in the mean (simply referred to as shifts hereafter). Both techniques were applied using the same reference series.

[17] The MLR test [Vincent, 1998] with two regression models for the detection of shifts was applied in this study; the other two models for the detection of trends [Vincent, 1998] were not used. The dependent variable was the candidate series (tested series) while the independent variable was the reference series (neighbor series). An additional independent variable was added to the model to describe a potential shift in the candidate series. When the date k of the shift is unknown, it is necessary to find the date k that corresponds to the minimum sum of squared residuals, namely, the most probable date k for a shift. The statistical significance of the most probable shift is determined using a maximal F test statistic. When a significant shift is detected, the time series is divided at the date of the shift, and each segment (before and after the shift) is re-tested separately. The procedure was repeated until all the segments of the series were found to be homogeneous.

[18] The PMTred algorithm [Wang, 2008] is based on the PMT test [Wang *et al.*, 2007] for detecting unknown shifts in time series of no temporal trend. It also searches for the most probable position of shift in a segment of the series being tested and tests its statistical significance using a penalized maximal t test statistic, in which the lag-1 autocorrelation is also accounted for. Because the time series being tested is assumed to have no temporal trends, the PMTred algorithm needs to use a reference series to represent trends and low-frequency variations in the candidate series. The PMTred algorithm is applied to the time series of the differences between the candidate and reference series. Different from this, the MLR technique uses the reference series as a regression variable, so that trends and low-frequency variations are to be accounted by the regression relationship between the candidate and the reference series, to be diminished from the residual series. Other differences between the MLR and PMTred methods include: (1) PMTred accounts for the effects of unequal lengths of the two segments before and after a shift and thereby has higher detection power [Wang *et al.*, 2007]; (2) PMTred has a re-recursive testing procedure for detecting multiple change points in a single time series [Wang, 2008], and (3) PMTred accounts for lag-1 autocorrelation which are often non-negligible for climate

data time series and thereby reduces the number of false alarms [Wang, 2008].

[19] The MLR test is implemented using a simple FORTRAN program, with the results and time series being plotted and examined using Microsoft Excel. The PMTred algorithm is implemented using the RHtestsV3 software package [Wang and Feng, 2009]. This package includes plots of the relevant time series and the resulting estimates of shifts and trends in the candidate series, which are very helpful for its users. Both approaches were applied for the identification of shifts in individual candidate series. Shifts detection was performed on de-seasonalized series of monthly means of daily maximum and of daily minimum temperatures separately.

[20] Three to seven suitable neighbors were used individually as reference series. The neighbor selection was based on the proximity of the candidate station, correlation and period of data. It was possible to find relatively close and well correlated neighbors for a period of 30 to 40 years, but it was much more difficult for longer periods of time. For the second generation data set, most neighbors were within 200 km; however, they were occasionally as far as 700 km in the north. The correlation on annual values was mainly greater than 0.70 (this is in agreement with the findings of North *et al.* [2011] who have shown that correlation between annual averaged station's surface air temperature decays in a near-exponential fashion as a function of distance). When MLR and PMTred were applied using the same neighbor, the dates of the detected shifts were usually the same; but on occasion, PMTred identified additional shifts. However, the dates were sometimes very different when various neighbors were used. This could arise from inhomogeneities in some of the neighbor series (neighbor stations with known inhomogeneities were not necessary excluded depending on the date when their inhomogeneities occurred), in addition to statistical estimation error. Common shifts (identified by at least two neighbors) were retained and analyzed. The related metadata was examined for the detected shifts, along with the plots of time series and the corresponding regression fits, to determine whether the identified shifts were in the candidate series or in reference series.

[21] The homogenization process in Canada was largely based on statistical testing in order to minimize the use of the station history files [Vincent, 1998; Gullett *et al.*, 1991]. Such files are often retained as paper copies only: there are bulky, aged, awkward to handle physically, and the information can be sparse and incomplete. Recently, some inspector reports have been digitized, but this has been done only for a small number stations (of the 338 stations in the second generation data sets), and mainly for the most recent period of time. Still, even though incomplete, metadata is consulted whenever possible, as greater confidence is usually placed in the data adjustments if the detected shifts are supported with historical information.

[22] A detailed typical example is presented. As shown in Figure 4, shifts were detected in the monthly mean anomalies of the daily maximum temperature at Brockville, Ontario, using four neighbors. The distance between the candidate series (Brockville) and neighbor 1, 2, 3 and 4 was 54, 144, 104 and 186 km respectively; the correlation on annual values was 0.73, 0.79, 0.71 and 0.88, while the correlation on the first difference series was 0.96, 0.94, 0.95, and 0.94.

The results are examined starting with the most recent changepoint. It is important to point out that all these dates except 1938 were detected by both techniques. A first changepoint was detected in 1994 with neighbor 1 and 2, and 2000 and 2001 with neighbor 3 and 4. The metadata revealed that there was a relocation of the instruments in 1994, 150 m from the old site to improve exposure. Since there was no indication of change for 2000 or 2001, 1994 was kept as the first changepoint. A second shift was identified in 1965 with neighbor 1 and 3, and in 1962 with neighbor 2 and 4. Observations from two sites were merged in 1965 (the sites were 2.6 km apart with a difference in elevation of 5 m). Although there was no indication of change in 1962 in the metadata, both 1962 and 1965 were kept as changepoints, because the shift in 1962 is visually apparent with all neighbors: it also appears to be associated with a change in variance and coincides with a data gap (in this case, it is more likely that the metadata is incomplete). The third shift in 1951 (or 1950) which was identified with neighbor 2, 3 and 4; however, we did not find any cause for this shift in the metadata. The changepoint in 1938 was detected with only one technique (PMTred) with only one neighbor and it is not supported by metadata: therefore this changepoint was not kept for adjustment. Since the neighbor 3 and 4 data series are too short to be used for identification of any shifts before 1930, the changepoint in 1928 was identified with neighbor 1 and 2 only. Although it was not supported by metadata, it is visually apparent (Figure 4) and thus was kept for adjustment. Thus, five changepoints (1994, 1965, 1962, 1951, and 1928) were retained for the Brockville series. In summary, a changepoint was generally retained when it was detected by both methods, with at least two neighbors, and preferably with metadata support.

[23] The same procedure using both techniques was used to identify shifts in the de-seasonalized monthly means of daily maximum temperatures and of daily minimum temperatures, respectively, at each of the 338 locations. The total number of detected shifts is reported in Table 1. It is important to clarify here that "no shifts" indicates that the series was found to be homogeneous: no shifts were retained for adjustment because there was no agreement among the detection results by both methods with different neighbors, and no supported metadata. About 66% (64%) of the stations have no shifts in their maximum (minimum) temperature and are considered homogeneous (thus they do not need adjustment). Sometimes shifts were identified on the same dates in both the maximum and minimum temperatures. Overall, for 190 locations both the maximum and minimum temperature series were found to be homogeneous. Table 1 also gives the causes of the shifts that are kept for adjustment. About 70% of the shifts have an identified cause including: joining of observations at co-located sites, instruments relocation (the station has kept the same identification number), and other causes such as change in observer, instruments and automation. About 30% of the shifts were adjusted although there was no metadata support (and in these cases, metadata was deemed to be incomplete, as for the 1962 shift in Figure 4). Figure 5 shows the distributions of the years of shifts identified in these series. A 1942/1943 shift occurred at 12 (10) out of the 20 joining dates for maximum (minimum) temperature; this shift was mainly due to relocation of sites to airports. A 1994/1995/1996 shift occurred in 9 (10) out of the 24

Figure 4. Difference between the monthly mean anomalies of the tested station Brockville, Ontario, and 4 neighbor stations along with the detected change points.

joining dates for maximum (minimum) temperature and was mostly related to automation (including relocation of the instruments).

2.5. Adjustment of Monthly Temperature for Non-climatic Shifts

[24] In the first generation data sets, a procedure based on regression models was used to obtain monthly adjustments [Vincent *et al.*, 2002] (hereafter referred as MRs for Monthly Regressions). Regression models were applied to the time series for each of the 12 individual calendar months in order to produce 12 monthly adjustments (one for each calendar month). The dependent and independent variables were the temperature of the candidate and neighbor series, respectively, and an additional independent variable was used to provide the monthly shift size when a shift is detected. For each calendar month, different estimates of the monthly shift sizes were obtained using different neighbors, and the average of these estimates was taken as the final estimate of the monthly shift size (gray bars in Figure 6a). A polynomial of degree two was then applied to the 12 monthly adjustments in order to produce 12 smoothed monthly adjustments (black line in Figure 6a). A period of 20 years before and after each shift was usually used for the regression models, however the period was sometimes shortened due to inhomogeneities in the candidate and neighbor series.

[25] In the second generation data sets, monthly adjustments were derived from a recently developed Quantile-Matching

(QM) adjustment algorithm so that the empirical distributions of the monthly mean temperatures, before and after each shift, match each other [Wang *et al.*, 2010]. The procedure can be summarized as follows. Let $C_{bef,t}$ and $C_{aft,t}$ denote a segment of the candidate temperature series (up to 10 years in length) before and after the shift, respectively; and $R_{bef,t}$ and $R_{aft,t}$ the corresponding segments of the reference (a neighbor) temperature series. The $C_{bef,t}$ are first ranked and

Table 1. Number of Stations With No, One, Two, Three and Four Shifts Adjusted for Minimum And Maximum Temperature and Number of Shifts Due to Different Causes

	Maximum Temperature	Minimum Temperature
Number of stations with:		
No shift	224	218
One shift	71	73
Two shifts	31	32
Three shifts	8	12
Four shifts	4	3
Total number of stations	338	338
Number of shifts due to:		
Joining observations	72	78
Station / instruments relocation	33	33
Other causes	13	20
No corresponding metadata	55	54
Total number of shifts	173	185

Figure 5. Frequency of the shifts identified in the series of monthly mean daily maximum temperatures (114 series/173 shifts) and daily minimum temperatures (120 series/185 shifts).

divided into M_q quantile-categories (here $M_q = 12$), and so are the $C_{aft,t}$. The temperature differences between the candidate and reference sites before the shift, $D_{bef,t} = C_{bef,t} - R_{bef,t}$, are binned according to the category in which $C_{bef,t}$ falls; similarly, the differences, $D_{aft,t} = C_{aft,t} - R_{aft,t}$, are binned according to the category in which $C_{aft,t}$ falls. The category-averages of the $D_{bef,t}$ ($D_{aft,t}$) are calculated for each quantile category before (after) the shift. Finally, the differences between each pair of category-averages (before and after the shift) are obtained for each category (gray bars in Figure 6b) and a natural spline is fitted to these M_q category-average differences (black line in Figure 6b). The natural spline is used to estimate QM adjustments. For example, the QM adjustment for value $C_{bef,t}$ is the value of the spline corresponding to the cumulative frequency of the value $C_{bef,t}$. Therefore, QM adjustments are usually different for temperatures of different cumulative frequencies; they might be the same if the non-climatic effect is the same across the

whole distribution (a true mean shift). In this study, the reference series was provided from the best correlated neighbor having the longest homogeneous period of time surrounding the shift to be adjusted.

[26] The means of all monthly adjustments calculated from the MRs and QM procedures are very similar over an adjusted period. However, the QM adjustments have the property of being year-dependent as they differ according to where the monthly temperature value stands in the probability distribution. For example, for Brockville, the MRs procedure suggests that all January values of the homogeneous period prior 1965 be adjusted by about -0.3°C regardless if it was a cold or warm January (Figure 6a). On the other hand, the QM adjustments for the January temperatures (which fall in the lower 20-percentiles of the distribution) range from about -0.4 to -0.9°C (Figure 6b) depending if it is a warm or cold January (the QM adjustment for a warm January is different from that for a cold January). Annual

Figure 6. MRs and QM monthly adjustments for the changepoints 1965 at Brockville, Ontario. For the MRs adjustments, a polynomial of degree two (black) is fitted to the monthly shifts (gray) in order to produce 12 smoothed monthly adjustments (given at mid-point of each calendar month). For the QM adjustments, the difference between the 12 quantile categories, before and after 1965, is obtained (gray) for the cumulative frequency distribution along with the corresponding natural spline (black). The low frequencies correspond to cold winter months while high frequencies are associated to warm summer months.

Figure 7. Annual mean of the daily maximum temperatures for Brockville, Ontario, before (gray – dashed line) and after (black – solid line) QM adjustment.

trends obtained at individual stations adjusted by the MRs and QM procedures are very similar over the same period of time: however, further testing is required to fully compare the MRs and QM adjustments. The annual mean series of Brockville daily maximum temperatures before and after QM adjustments are shown in Figure 7 (for which five changepoints were detected and adjusted for this series; see section 2.4).

[27] The QM procedure was applied to adjust monthly temperature series for the 173 and 185 shifts detected in maximum and minimum temperatures, respectively (Table 1). Whereas instrument relocations and other changes occurred at observing sites can cause either a rise or a drop in the observed temperature, the magnitude of all changes is not necessary symmetrical about zero. Figure 8 shows the frequency distribution of the monthly QM adjustments applied to the monthly mean series of the daily maximum or minimum temperatures. The vast majority of the adjustments vary from -3.0 to 3.0°C . The average of the monthly QM adjustments is -0.35°C for the maximum temperature data set and -0.29°C for the minimum temperature data set. This asymmetry is partly due to a decreasing shift often detected in the mid-1940s caused by the joining of station observations and relocations of the instruments at new airports. About 75%

of the airport sites were located at a higher elevation than the original site, and the join of the station observations (or the instruments' relocation) have created a decreasing step in the unadjusted temperature time series due to colder temperature at the more elevated airport site. In general, instruments were often relocated to sites with better exposure, away from pavement and nearby buildings, creating a non-climatic decreasing step in their unadjusted temperature time series.

3. Trends Analysis

[28] Trends in annual and seasonal means of daily maximum, minimum and mean temperatures were examined at individual stations and for the country (the daily mean temperature is the average of the daily maximum and minimum). Since the climate observing network in the northern regions was established only during the late 1940s, there are very few locations in the north with temperature data prior to 1945. For this reason, the trends were examined for two periods: 1950–2010 for Canada (the entire country) and 1900–2010 for Southern Canada (south of 60°N). In addition, for the computation of average spatial trends, observations from the irregularly distributed climate stations had to be interpolated to evenly spaced grid point locations for equal representation across the country. Therefore, the monthly, seasonal, and annual temperature anomalies (departures from the 1961–1990 average) obtained at individual stations were interpolated to the 50 km spaced grid points (CANGRD, E. Milewska and R. D. Whitewood, Tool for monitoring areal climate trends in Canada, unpublished manuscript, 2011) using the statistical method of Gandin's Optimal Interpolation [Gandin, 1965; Bretherton *et al.*, 1976; Alaka and Elvander, 1972]. Seasonal and annual grid point values were then averaged to produce the annual and seasonal time series for Canada and Southern Canada. All linear trends were estimated using the approach by Sen [1968] and the statistical significance of the trend was assessed at the 5% confidence level using the Kendall's test [Kendall, 1955]. Trends at the stations were computed only if more than 80% of the values were present in the series.

Figure 8. Frequency distribution of the QM adjustments applied to the monthly mean of the daily maximum or minimum temperatures (for the 173 and 185 shifts detected in the maximum and minimum temperature, respectively).

Table 2. Annual and Seasonal Temperature Trends for Canada 1950–2010 (°C/61 Years) and for Southern Canada 1900–2010 (°C/111 Years)

Period	Season	Maximum Temperature	Minimum Temperature	Mean Temperature
1950–2010	annual	1.4	1.7	1.5
	winter	2.1	2.7	2.3
	spring	1.6	1.9	1.7
	summer	1.0	1.2	1.1
	fall	1.3	1.6	1.4
1900–2010	annual	1.0	2.1	1.5
	winter	1.8	3.2	2.5
	spring	1.5	2.4	1.9
	summer	0.9	1.9	1.4
	fall	0.5	1.6	1.0

3.1. The 1950–2010 Trends in Canada

[29] The annual mean temperature in Canada has increased by about 1.5°C over 1950–2010 (Table 2). This warming is slightly more pronounced in the nighttime temperature (daily minimum) than the daytime temperature (daily maximum): the trends in maximum and minimum temperature are 1.4°C and 1.7°C, respectively, for the 61 years. The national series indicate that 2010 was the warmest year on record followed by 2006 and 1998, and the coldest year was 1972 (Figure 9).

Positive trends are observed at almost all locations across the country: about 63% and 67% of the stations show significant increasing trends in their daytime and nighttime temperature, respectively (Figure 10). The nighttime warming is slightly greater than the daytime warming at most locations: the majority of the annual trends vary from 0.3 to 3.0°C in minimum temperature and from 0.3 to 2.5°C in maximum temperature.

[30] The seasonal mean temperature trends for Canada indicate that the greatest temperature change occurs during the winter with a positive trend of 2.3°C for 1950–2010 (Table 2). Spatially, the winter warming is mainly found in the western regions and in the south whereas several non-significant decreasing trends are identified in the east (Figure 10). At individual stations, most increasing trends range from 1.0 to more than 5.0°C over the 61 years for both winter daytime and nighttime temperature. During the spring, the magnitude of the warming is smaller but still considerable: the national series shows an increase of 1.7°C in mean temperature for 1950–2010. Even if increasing trends are observed at most locations across the country, there are still a few stations showing non-significant decrease in the eastern regions, particularly in nighttime temperature. Increasing spring temperature trends vary from 0.5 to 3.5°C over the past 61 years

Figure 9. Annual mean maximum and minimum temperature anomalies for Canada, 1950–2010, and Southern Canada, 1900–2010.

Figure 10. Trends in annual and seasonal mean of the daily maximum and minimum temperature for 1950–2010. Upward (red) and downward (blue) pointing triangles indicate positive and negative trends respectively. Filled triangles correspond to trends significant at the 5% level. The size of the triangle is proportional to the magnitude of the trend.

at most locations and for both daytime and nighttime temperature.

[31] The warming in Canada is much weaker during the summer and fall. The national time series indicate an increase of 1.1°C in the summer mean temperature over 1950–2010 (Table 2). Spatially, the summer warming is observed across the country and most locations have trends ranging from 0.3 to 2.5°C for the past 61 years; however, there are still a number of locations showing non-significant decreasing trends in the Canadian Prairies, particularly for the daytime temperature (Figure 10). In the fall, there is a distinct pattern of mixed non-significant decreasing and increasing trends in the south (although that several significant increasing trends are also found in nighttime temperature) and significant increasing trends in the north and east. The significant trends during the fall vary from 1.0 to 3.5°C for the last 61 years in the northern and eastern regions. Overall, the national series indicates that the fall temperature has increased by 1.4°C over 1950–2010.

3.2. The 1900–2010 Trends in Southern Canada

[32] The annual mean temperature for Southern Canada has increased by 1.5°C for 1900–2010 (Table 2). The warming is considerably greater in the nighttime temperature compare to the daytime temperature: annual trends of 2.1°C and 1.0°C are observed over the past 111 years in the minimum and maximum temperatures, respectively. The annual nighttime temperature for Southern Canada shows a steady increase from the beginning to the end of the period whereas the daytime temperature indicates an increase from the 1900s to the beginning of the 1940s, followed by a slight decrease to the 1970s, and a considerable increase until 2010 (Figure 9). Although there are fewer stations in Southern Canada with enough data to compute the trends from 1900 to 2010 than for the shorter period, 63% and 92% of the long-term stations show a significant increase in their annual maximum and minimum temperature, respectively (Figure 11). At individual stations, the annual trends generally vary from 1.0°C to 3.5°C for nighttime temperature while they range from 0.5°C to 2.5°C for daytime temperature for 1900–2010.

[33] The seasonal trends for Southern Canada indicate that the greatest temperature change over the past 111 years also occur during the winter when the mean temperature increased by 2.5°C (Table 2). The temperature trend pattern is very

Figure 11. Trends in annual mean of the daily maximum and minimum temperature for 1900–2010. Upward (red) and downward (blue) pointing triangles indicate positive and negative trends respectively. Filled triangles correspond to trends significant at the 5% level. The size of the triangle is proportional to the magnitude of the trend.

similar for winter and spring over the 1900–2010 period: almost all locations across the country have a significant positive trend. At most stations, the winter and spring trends vary from 2.0°C to more than 5.0°C for the minimum temperature and from 1.5°C to 4.5°C for maximum temperature. The warming in Southern Canada is much less during the summer and fall. During these two seasons, most stations show a significant increasing trend of 1.0 to 3.0°C in their nighttime temperature over the past 111 years whereas a mixed pattern of non-significant decreasing and increasing trends, and few significant increasing trends is observed in the daytime temperature across the country for 1900–2010.

4. Discussion

[34] In this study, the detection of changepoints was performed on the monthly temperature series of individual stations using two techniques, several neighbors and metadata. It took a considerable amount of time to assess the time series of 338 stations, maximum and minimum temperature separately, since the approach taken in this study requires making decisions in order to determine which of the detected shifts needs adjustment. The advantages were to be able to record the causes of inhomogeneities when available and to increase our understanding of their impact on temperature. Automated homogenization procedures have been recently developed to accelerate detection on monthly mean temperature time series [Menne and Williams, 2009; Szentimrey, 2008]. These procedures automatically identify changepoints through mutual comparison of series within the same climate region and they do not assume that the neighbor series are homogeneous. Although fully automated algorithms are highly desirable, local homogenized data prepared with some level of manual intervention are still needed to better understand the causes of inhomogeneities in temperature series and for use in validation of automated procedures.

[35] It was found in this study that about 65% of the time series were homogeneous. This seems to be a large number of homogeneous series as compared to results from other regions [Venema et al., 2012]. Canada is a vast country with a relatively small number of stations covering long periods of time. A main challenge for homogeneity testing in Canada is that neighbor stations are usually far (within 200 km, and they can be as far as 700 km in the north). Since a shift was retained for adjustment only if it was identified with at least two neighbors, then many stations were declared homogeneous. About 60% of the stations were also found homogeneous in the first generation data sets [Vincent and Gullett, 1999].

[36] It is difficult to compare this new version of the data sets to the earlier version in terms of the frequency of adjustments since the input data are not the same. The number of stations is different (210 stations for the first generation and 338 stations for the second generation); the length of the time series is different (time series ending in early 2000s were tested for homogeneity in the first generation data sets while time series ending in 2010 were tested in the second generation data sets); in addition, the joining years and neighbors were sometimes different. Overall, for the same stations, same length of time series, same joining years and same neighbors, the frequency of the adjustments were the same.

[37] Trends calculated before and after adjustments were compared at individual stations. Since shifts were detected at various dates in time (Figure 5) and adjustments were either positive or negative (Figure 8), the impact of adjustments on the trends varies from station to station and for different periods of time (Figure 7). Overall, the adjustments that have affected the trends most were those for the change in observing time in 1961. In this case, the daily minimum temperature of many stations (120 stations) was adjusted for the decreasing step in 1961 (Figure 3). At these stations, the trends generally became more positive or reversing from negative to positive with the adjustments – in particular in the eastern regions of the country [Vincent et al., 2009].

[38] There exist a very limited number of techniques for homogenizing daily climate data series. This is because daily data are much more variable spatially and seasonally; they are notably influenced by topography and local surroundings [Trewin and Trevitt, 1996]. Nonetheless, a few innovative techniques have been recently developed [Della-Marta and Wanner, 2006; Toreti et al., 2010; Wang et al. 2010; Mestre et al., 2011] and have been applied to daily temperatures [Kuglitsch et al., 2009; Brown et al., 2010; Nemeč et al., 2012]. Still, more work is needed to evaluate and compare methods for homogenizing daily temperatures and especially to determine the impact of automation [Guttman and Baker, 1996; Milewska and Hogg, 2002; Sun et al., 2005]. The QM algorithm using a reference series is currently being tested for adjusting daily temperature in a region where the neighboring series can be relatively far and of a weaker correlation with the candidate series (such as found in Canada). After that, the QM algorithm will be used to adjust the daily temperatures of the Canadian stations for the shifts identified in the monthly series. This work on developing the second generation of homogenized daily temperatures will be reported in a separate study. For the time being, daily temperatures have been adjusted for the non-climatic shifts detected in the monthly temperature series in the current study using linear interpolation between the monthly adjustments (similarly to Vincent et al. [2002]); these homogenized daily temperatures are available from the lead author upon request.

5. Concluding Remarks

[39] Homogenized temperature time series data set was prepared for the analysis of trends at 338 locations across Canada. The various tasks involved can be summarized as follows:

[40] 1. Data of two, three or four co-located sites were combined together in order to produce longer time series. This was done at 63% of the stations (213 stations).

[41] 2. Daily minimum temperatures were adjusted for the change in observing time in July 1961 using a procedure based on hourly temperature observations. This affected daily minimum temperatures for the period 1961–2010 at about 36% of the stations (120 synoptic stations).

[42] 3. Monthly mean temperature anomalies were tested for temporal homogeneity using two statistical methods with neighboring stations. As a result, 66% of the maximum temperature series (224 stations) and 64% of the minimum temperature series (218 stations) were found to be homogeneous (no adjustments needed). A total of 190 stations did not

require any homogeneity adjustments for either the maximum or the minimum temperature series.

[43] 4. For temperature series with detected non-climatic shifts, the monthly mean series of daily maximum and/or minimum temperatures were adjusted to be in agreement with the most recent homogeneous part of the series in terms of temporal homogeneity. Such adjustments were applied to the maximum temperature series at 114 stations for a total of 173 shifts, and to the minimum temperature series at 120 stations for a total of 185 shifts.

[44] Several improvements were made in the second generation of homogenized temperature data sets as compared to the first generation. The station list was revised to include more locations with better spatial and temporal coverage. The temperature data of more co-located sites were joined together in order to produce a greater number of longer data time series. For the change in observing time in 1961, adjustments were applied to the affected daily minimum temperatures using an improved procedure based on hourly temperatures, whereas every day was adjusted in the first generation data sets using a procedure based on statistically estimated monthly adjustments. Homogeneity testing and adjustments were done thoroughly including the full period of record at each station in the second generation data sets whereas it was done on records with data up to the beginning of the 2000s in the first generation data sets. Two techniques were used to detect non-climatic shifts in de-seasonalized monthly mean of daily maximum and minimum temperature series separately in order to confirm the position in time of the non-climatic shifts. A new procedure based on a Quantile-Matching algorithm was used to obtain better estimates of the monthly adjustments.

[45] Annual and seasonal temperature trends were examined using the resulting homogenized data sets. The results show that the temperature has increased in Canada over the past 61 years (1950–2010) and that the warming is slightly more pronounced in the minimum temperature than in the maximum temperature over this period of time. The results are similar for Southern Canada although the warming is considerably greater in the minimum temperature compared to the maximum temperature over the past 111 years (1900–2010). Warming temperature is generally observed in all seasons and the greatest warming is found in winter and spring for both periods. Overall, similar results were found in Zhang *et al.* [2000]. In their study, the results showed an increase in temperature slightly greater in the minimum than in the maximum temperature for Canada over the period 1950–1998, and much more pronounced in the minimum temperature as compared to the maximum temperature for Southern Canada for 1900–1998. Their findings also showed that seasonally, the greatest warming was observed during winter and spring compared to summer and fall for both periods, which is in agreement with the findings of the current study.

[46] In conclusion, as of today, the second generation of homogenized monthly surface air temperature provides the best data sets for temperature trends in Canada along with detailed documentation on how the data sets were prepared. It is important to encourage homogenization work carried out by scientists who are likely to have access to local data and metadata and who are familiar with their own local geography and climate variations. Homogenized data sets

prepared at regional and national level can be helpful to complete and validate large/global homogenized data sets prepared by the scientific community. The Second Generation of Homogenized Canadian Monthly Surface Air Temperature is now available as part of the Adjusted and Homogenized Canadian Climate Data (AHCCD) at <http://www.ec.gc.ca/dcca-ahccd/>.

[47] **Acknowledgments.** The authors would like to thank Francis Zwiers from the Pacific Climate Impacts Consortium, University of Victoria, Canada, and Xuebin Zhang and Eva Mekis from the Climate Research Division, Sciences and Technologies Branch of Environment Canada, as well as three anonymous reviewers for their helpful comments and suggestions that have helped improve the manuscript.

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Observed Trends in Canada's Climate and Influence of Low-Frequency Variability Modes

L. A. VINCENT, X. ZHANG, R. D. BROWN, Y. FENG, E. MEKIS, E. J. MILEWSKA,
H. WAN, AND X. L. WANG

Climate Research Division, Science and Technology Branch, Environment Canada, Toronto, Ontario, Canada

(Manuscript received 10 October 2014, in final form 23 January 2015)

ABSTRACT

Trends in Canada's climate are analyzed using recently updated data to provide a comprehensive view of climate variability and long-term changes over the period of instrumental record. Trends in surface air temperature, precipitation, snow cover, and streamflow indices are examined along with the potential impact of low-frequency variability related to large-scale atmospheric and oceanic oscillations on these trends. The results show that temperature has increased significantly in most regions of Canada over the period 1948–2012, with the largest warming occurring in winter and spring. Precipitation has also increased, especially in the north. Changes in other climate and hydroclimatic variables, including a decrease in the amount of precipitation falling as snow in the south, fewer days with snow cover, an earlier start of the spring high-flow season, and an increase in April streamflow, are consistent with the observed warming and precipitation trends. For the period 1900–2012, there are sufficient temperature and precipitation data for trend analysis for southern Canada (south of 60°N) only. During this period, temperature has increased significantly across the region, precipitation has increased, and the amount of precipitation falling as snow has decreased in many areas south of 55°N. The results also show that modes of low-frequency variability modulate the spatial distribution and strength of the trends; however, they alone cannot explain the observed long-term trends in these climate variables.

1. Introduction

Over the past several decades, the northern regions have experienced some of the most rapid warming on Earth (Alexander et al. 2013; Houghton et al. 2001). The annual mean temperature over the high-latitude land area has increased by almost twice the rate of the global average (AMAP-SWIPA 2011; Anisimov et al. 2007; ACIA 2005). The cause of the warming amplification in the northern regions has been attributed primarily to temperature and albedo feedbacks because of complex interactions between land surface temperature, snow cover or sea ice extent, and the atmosphere (Pithan and Mauritsen 2014; Serreze and Barry 2011). Canada, with a large northern landmass, is also experiencing rapid warming with nationwide annual mean surface air

temperature increasing by 1.5°C over the period 1950–2010 (Vincent et al. 2012). This warming has been accompanied by significant changes in many other climate elements, in different parts of the country, including increases in precipitation (Mekis and Vincent 2011), decreases in the duration of snow cover (Brown and Braaten 1998), and decreases in streamflow (Zhang et al. 2001). These changes in Canada's climate have widespread impacts on the environment, economic activities, and human health, especially in the north, where warming is proceeding more rapidly and where ecosystems and traditional lifestyles are particularly sensitive to warming (Warren and Lemmen 2014; Allard and Lemay 2012).

Recent changes in Canada's climate have been attributed, at least in part, to the increase in the concentration of atmospheric greenhouse gases associated with anthropogenic activities. Evidence of an anthropogenic influence was found on temperature in the southern regions of Canada (Zhang et al. 2006), in the Arctic (Najafi et al. 2015; Gillett et al. 2008), on Arctic sea ice and precipitation (Min et al. 2008a,b), and to a lesser extent on heavy precipitation events over a large part of the Northern Hemisphere land areas (Min et al. 2011).

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Corresponding author address: Lucie Vincent, Climate Research Division, Science and Technology Branch, Environment Canada, 4905 Dufferin Street, Toronto ON M3H 5T4, Canada.
E-mail: lucie.vincent@ec.gc.ca

DOI: 10.1175/JCLI-D-14-00697.1

Barnett et al. (2008) attributed much of the observed changes during the second half of the twentieth century seen in winter surface air temperature, river flow, and snowpack in the western United States to anthropogenic forcing.

Previous studies have documented significant links between low-frequency modes of atmospheric–oceanic variability and Canadian climate. For example, positive phases of the Pacific decadal oscillation (PDO) and El Niño–Southern Oscillation (ENSO) have been associated with warm winter temperatures in western and central Canada (Shabbar and Yu 2012; Bonsal et al. 2001; Shabbar and Khandekar 1996) and a reduction of snow cover in western Canada (Brown 1998). An abrupt transition to lower snow depths in the mid-1970s was related to a shift in the Pacific–North America (PNA) index (Brown and Braaten 1998). Interannual variations in Canadian Prairies precipitation have been associated with ENSO variations (Bonsal and Lawford 1999; Shabbar et al. 1997). Positive phases of the PNA pattern and PDO corresponded to shorter durations of ice cover on lakes and rivers (Bonsal et al. 2006), increasing streamflow regime in spring (Brabets and Walvoord 2009), and earlier high-flow season (Stewart et al. 2005). Trends toward positive modes of the North Atlantic Oscillation (NAO) were associated with cold and dry winters in northeastern Canada (Bonsal et al. 2001). Brown (2010) documented evidence of an abrupt decrease in snow depth in southern Quebec around 1980 linked to a reduction in the number of winter storms over the region (Wang et al. 2006) coinciding with a transition to more positive values of the NAO.

It is important to improve our understanding of the various mechanisms responsible for changes in regional surface climate. Large-scale oscillations have a significant influence on climate trends: at times, they can mask or enhance the trends depending on the phase of the oscillation and the time period selected for trend analysis. Canada's climate shows multidecadal-scale variability over the past century associated with oceanic and atmospheric modes: the relationships are however regionally based and are more evident during the boreal winter. Canada's climate has also been influenced by anthropogenic warming in recent decades. It is therefore a complex task to estimate the magnitude of climate trends and their potential causes.

The first objective of this study is to provide a comprehensive analysis of the climate trends in Canada, including those for temperature, precipitation, snow-cover, and streamflow indices using recently updated data, and to highlight the consistency among the trends in related climate variables over similar periods of time. The second objective is to evaluate the climate trends

after removing the potential effects of low-frequency variability modes in order to determine if the trends remain significant and if they become more consistent across the country. To this end, climate trends are reassessed when indices of large-scale oscillations are used as explanatory variables in the trend estimation. Section 2 describes the datasets and section 3 presents the methodology. The trends in Canada's climate are described in section 4. The climate trends after removing the influence of low-frequency variability modes are provided in section 5. A summary and discussion follow in section 6.

2. Data

A number of data-related issues arise when attempting to analyze climate trends in Canada. There have been changes in instrumentation, observing practices, and relocation of observing sites that have introduced non-climatic variations in climate datasets (also called “inhomogeneities”), which can interfere with the proper assessment of any climate trends. In addition, the climate observing surface network in Canada has changed considerably in the past, especially since the 1990s, because of the downsizing of the traditional observing network and the increased use of automated systems (Milewska and Hogg 2002). Extensive research has been carried out over the past 15 yr to develop adjusted and homogenized surface air temperature, precipitation, wind speed, and pressure data for Canada to address many of the above concerns (Vincent et al. 2012; Mekis and Vincent 2011; Wan et al. 2010, 2007). However, more work is still needed, especially to address the issues related to the introduction of automated systems for precipitation.

a. Surface air temperature

Homogenized daily maximum and minimum temperatures for 338 locations across the country were retrieved from the second generation of homogenized temperature dataset (Vincent et al. 2012). Observations at collocated sites were sometimes joined in order to create longer time series for use in trend analysis. Daily temperatures from automatic systems were included at some stations. Two types of adjustments were performed to produce homogenized datasets. Daily minimum temperature recorded at 120 synoptic stations (mainly airports) was first adjusted to account for the bias due to the change in observing time in July 1961 (Vincent et al. 2009). A second adjustment based on the quantile-matching algorithm, as applied in Wang et al. (2014), was performed as part of the homogeneity assessment carried out by Vincent et al. (2012) to address shifts due to site relocation and changes in observing practices. The daily mean temperature is derived from

the daily maximum and minimum. Monthly mean temperature is computed as the average of the daily means and is set to missing if more than five random or three consecutive daily values are missing. Seasonal and annual means are obtained if all corresponding monthly values are nonmissing. The seasons are defined as winter (December–February), spring (March–May), summer (June–August), and autumn (September–November).

b. Precipitation

Adjusted daily rainfall and snowfall amounts at 464 locations were taken from the second generation adjusted precipitation dataset (Mekis and Vincent 2011). The data were adjusted to account for known measurements issues such as wind undercatch, evaporation and wetting losses for each type of rain gauge (Devine and Mekis 2008), conversion to snow water equivalent from snow ruler measurements (Mekis and Brown 2010), trace observations, and accumulated amounts from several days. As for temperature, observations from nearby collocated stations were sometimes merged to produce longer time series (Vincent and Mekis 2009). Measurements from automatic systems were not included. The adjusted daily total precipitation is the sum of the adjusted rainfall and adjusted snow water equivalent. The monthly total precipitation is the sum of the adjusted daily total precipitation amounts following the previously defined rule for missing daily temperature. Seasonal and annual totals are obtained if all corresponding monthly values are nonmissing. Trends in the ratio of snowfall to total precipitation (hereinafter “snowfall ratio”) are also examined since they provide information regarding changes in solid precipitation, which is a very important climate characteristic in Canada. The snowfall ratio is defined as the total snowfall water equivalent divided by the total precipitation obtained for each season and annually and is expressed as a percentage.

c. Gridding temperature and precipitation data

Since stations recording temperature and precipitation observations are irregularly distributed across the country with more stations in the south than in the north, temperature and precipitation data were interpolated to evenly spaced point locations for a better spatial representation of the climate variations over the country. Seasonal and annual temperature anomalies from the 1961–90 reference period were first obtained at individual stations. They were interpolated to 50-km spaced grid points (E. Milewska and R. D. Whitewood 2011, unpublished manuscript) using the method of Gandin’s optimal interpolation (Gandin 1965; Bretherton et al. 1976; Alaka and Elvander 1972).

Normalized seasonal and annual precipitation anomalies (normalized by dividing the anomalies by the 1961–90 averages) and snowfall ratio were gridded using the same method. Seasonal and annual grid point values were averaged together in order to produce seasonal and annual time series representing the whole country. The spatial representativeness of the climate network in Canada and the uncertainty associated to the interpolation were assessed in previous studies (Milewska and Hogg 2001; Zhang et al. 2000).

d. Snow cover

Snow cover data were derived from daily snow depth observations made at climate and synoptic stations since the beginning of the 1950s. Most of the observations were made at open sites or near populated regions and may not be representative of the surrounding area, particularly in regions with higher terrain and forest cover. Nonetheless, these observations still represent a consistent measure of temporal and spatial variations in snow cover in Canada. The data were taken from an update of the Canadian snow cover data (Meteorological Service of Canada 2000), which includes data rescue of previously undigitized Canadian snow depth data and the reconstruction of missing values as outlined in Brown and Braaten (1998). These data were supplemented with daily snow depth observations from the Digital Climate Archive of Environment Canada to the end of the 2012/13 snow season. A homogeneity assessment of the observations was carried out by Brown and Braaten (1998) with little evidence of detectable inhomogeneities due to station relocations.

The snow cover variables selected for this analysis are the annual maximum snow depth; date of the annual maximum snow depth; and snow-cover duration (SCD), which is defined as the number of days with at least 2 cm of snow on the ground during the snow year (August–July). The SCD is also computed over the first (August–January) and second (February–July) halves of the snow year providing a more objective way to monitor snow-cover onset and disappearance than the beginning and ending dates of continuous snow cover (which are sensitive to the definition of “continuous” snow cover). The number of stations recording snow depth has seriously decreased since the mid-1990s. There are only 104 stations with sufficient data for trend analysis for 1950–2012 (allowing for 10 missing years). Snow cover data were not gridded since there are too few stations to adequately represent spatial variations over the entire country.

e. Streamflow

Streamflow data were retrieved from the Reference Hydrometric Basin Network of Environment Canada

(Zhang et al. 2001; Scott et al. 1999), which has been updated to 2012 and contains daily mean streamflow observations at 226 basins, mainly located in the south, with at least 20 yr of data. The streamflow variables selected for this analysis are annual maximum and minimum daily mean streamflow (annual highest and lowest daily mean river discharge; expressed in $\text{m}^3 \text{s}^{-1}$); annual, April, and September mean streamflow; starting date of spring freshet; and river ice freezeup and breakup dates. The starting date of the spring freshet (also called high-flow season) is the date when the cumulative sum of the difference between the daily mean streamflow and its climatology reaches a minimum during the hydrological year, from October to September (Liebmann et al. 2007). In this study, there are only 53 sites with streamflow data and 20 sites with river ice breakup and freezeup dates with sufficient data for trend analysis over 1950–2012. Because of the limited number of sites with river ice data in the past 53 yr, the trends in streamflow indices are also examined over the shorter 1967–2012 period at 57 sites.

f. Large-scale atmospheric and oceanic oscillation indices

Low-frequency modes of climate variability linked to the Pacific and Atlantic Oceans are investigated to assess their influence on long-term climate variations in Canada. Four main modes of variability are assessed: the North Pacific index (NPI), Pacific decadal oscillation, North Atlantic Oscillation, the Atlantic multidecadal oscillation (AMO). NPI represents Pacific Ocean-related atmospheric oscillations and is defined as the area-weighted sea level pressure over the region 30° – 65°N and 160°E – 140°W (Trenberth and Hurrell 1994); this index was further normalized for this study. PDO represents Pacific Ocean oscillations and is defined as standardized values of the leading principal component of the monthly sea surface temperature anomalies north of 20°N (Zhang et al. 1997; Mantua et al. 1997). In the Atlantic, atmospheric oscillations are provided by NAO that are based on the difference in normalized sea level pressure between the Azores and Iceland (Osborn 2011; Jones et al. 1997; Hurrell 1995). Atlantic oceanic oscillations are represented by AMO defined by the normalized and detrended Kaplan sea surface temperature in the North Atlantic Ocean over 0° – 70°N (Enfield et al. 2001). Monthly data for atmospheric and ocean oscillations were extracted from various publically available sources. ENSO is not used in this study since its high-frequency oscillations are not helpful for explaining long-term trends. Seasonal means of the oscillations' indices were computed following the season's definition used for temperature and precipitation (winter average

indices for NPI, NAO, PDO, and AMO are presented in Fig. 1).

3. Methodology

Since the climate observing network in the northern regions was established during the late 1940s, there are very few locations in the north with observations prior to 1948. For this reason, temperature and precipitation trends are examined for two periods: 1948–2012 for Canada (the entire country) and 1900–2012 for southern Canada (south of 60°N). The trends for snow-cover and streamflow indices were analyzed for 1950–2012. The trend calculation methodology follows Zhang et al. (2000) with slope estimation from Sen (1968) and statistical significance based on the nonparametric Kendall's test (Kendall 1955). This test is less sensitive to the nonnormality of the data distribution and less affected by extreme values and outliers as compared to the commonly used least squares method. Since serial correlation is often present in climatological time series, the method involves an iterative procedure that takes into account the lag-1 autocorrelation of the time series (Zhang et al. 2000). The temperature and precipitation trends are computed at each grid point and for the time series averaged over Canada and southern Canada. The trends for the snow-cover and streamflow indices are obtained at individual stations. The statistical significance of the trends is assessed at the 5% level (statistically significant trends are reported as significant trends in the text). The uncertainty related to the linear trend is quantified using the 95% confidence interval (reported in square brackets in the text).

A multivariate regression modeling approach was used to evaluate the degree to which low-frequency variability modes (represented by the large-scale oscillations) were able to explain annual and seasonal variations over the short and long periods of time. A regression model was first fitted to the data at each grid point (for temperature and precipitation) or each station (for snow-cover and streamflow indices). Two explanatory variables were used to represent the Pacific and Atlantic influence (e.g., the indices for PDO and NAO) and the dependent variable was the climate element (temperature, precipitation, snow-cover, or streamflow indices). Then the method based on the Kendall test (described above) was applied directly on the residuals at each grid point (or station) in order to estimate the trends after removing the effects of the low-frequency variability modes. Annual and seasonal grid point (or station) residuals were averaged together in order to produce a single time series of residuals representing the entire country (or southern Canada).

FIG. 1. Winter standardized anomalies of the (a) NPI, (b) NAO, (c) PDO, and (d) AMO indices for 1900–2012. The black line is an 11-yr running mean.

The NAO and PDO indices were first introduced in the regression model since their influence on the Canada's climate is well documented. The annual and seasonal time series of these two indices are not correlated in time and only exhibit a significant positive trend in winter PDO for 1948–2012 and a significant negative trend in winter NAO for 1900–2012. The same procedure is repeated when the NPI and NAO indices (representing atmospheric oscillations in the North Pacific and North Atlantic) and PDO and AMO indices (representing the Pacific and Atlantic oceanic oscillations) are introduced in the regression model in order to determine if the results are similar. It is important to note that the annual and seasonal time series of the PDO and NPI, or AMO and NAO, are significantly correlated in time but inversely and cannot be used in the same regression model. There was no evidence of significant trends in annual or seasonal time series of NPI and AMO over the 1948–2012 and 1900–2012 periods.

4. Observed climate trends in Canada

a. Trends in surface air temperature

Significant trends in annual mean temperature ranging from 1° to 3°C are found almost everywhere

across the nation for 1948–2012 (Fig. 2a). The anomalies averaged over the country indicate a significant increase of 1.7°C [1.1° – 2.3°C] over the past 65 yr (Fig. 2b). The national time series exhibits considerable variability, although a steady increase is observed from the beginning of the 1970s to 2012. Seasonally, the greatest warming is found during winter (Fig. 3a). The winter trends are predominant in the western regions (northern British Columbia and Alberta, Yukon, Northwest Territories, and western Nunavut), ranging from 4° to 6°C over the past 65 yr. In spring, the warming is less pronounced, but significant warming trends are also dominant over the western regions (Fig. 3b). Summer mean temperature has increased much less than the winter and spring mean temperatures, but the magnitude of the warming is generally more consistent across the country (Fig. 3c). During autumn (Fig. 3d), most of the warming is observed in the Arctic and northern Quebec. Seasonal mean temperature anomalies averaged over Canada indicate significant increases of 3.3° [1.8° – 4.8°C], 1.8° [0.7° – 3.0°C], 1.4° [0.8° – 1.8°C], and 1.5°C [0.5° – 2.6°C] over 1948–2012 for winter, spring, summer, and autumn, respectively.

The results for southern Canada (Fig. 2c) show significant warming across the entire region averaging

FIG. 2. Trends in annual mean temperature for (a) 1948–2012 [$^{\circ}\text{C} (65 \text{ yr})^{-1}$] and (c) 1900–2012 [$^{\circ}\text{C} (113 \text{ yr})^{-1}$]. Grid squares with trends statistically significant at the 5% level are marked with a dot. Annual mean temperature anomalies for (b) Canada (1948–2012) and (d) southern Canada (1900–2012). The black line is an 11-yr running mean.

$1.6^{\circ}\text{C} [1.2^{\circ}\text{--}2.0^{\circ}\text{C}]$ over the 1900–2012 period (Fig. 2d). The warming is not monotonic, with periods of more rapid increase evident prior to the 1940s and after the 1970s and with a modest cooling observed over 1940–70. The seasonal trend results (not shown) indicate significant warming in all seasons over southern Canada, averaging $2.6^{\circ} [1.4^{\circ}\text{--}3.8^{\circ}\text{C}]$, $1.9^{\circ} [1.1^{\circ}\text{--}2.7^{\circ}\text{C}]$, $1.4^{\circ} [1.1^{\circ}\text{--}1.8^{\circ}\text{C}]$, and $1.0^{\circ}\text{C} [0.3^{\circ}\text{--}1.8^{\circ}\text{C}]$ for winter, spring, summer, and autumn, respectively. The winter warming is more pronounced in the western regions (eastern British Columbia, Alberta, Saskatchewan, and western Manitoba), with trends of $2^{\circ}\text{--}4^{\circ}\text{C}$ over the 113-yr period. These trends are consistent with previous results (Vincent et al. 2012, 2007; Zhang et al. 2000) obtained over shorter periods of time. A reconstruction of global surface air temperature over 1901–2012 suggests that the greatest warming has occurred over northwestern North America and central Eurasia (Vose et al. 2012).

b. Trends in precipitation

Annual total precipitation has increased mainly in the northern regions during 1948–2012 (Yukon, Northwest Territories, Nunavut, and northern Quebec), although some areas in the south (eastern Manitoba, western and southern Ontario, and Atlantic Canada) have also experienced significant increasing trends (Fig. 4a). There is more spatial variability in precipitation trends than in temperature trends. The anomalies averaged over the country indicate a significant increase of 19% [$15\%\text{--}22\%$] during the past 65 yr (Fig. 4b). It is important to note that the percentage anomalies in the north represent much less precipitation amounts than the same percentage in the south. In all seasons, total precipitation has increased mainly in the north (Fig. 5). In winter, decreasing trends are dominant in the southwest (British Columbia, Alberta, and Saskatchewan). There is less evidence of significant changes in the south during spring, summer, and autumn.

FIG. 3. Trends in mean temperature for 1948–2012 for (a) winter, (b) spring, (c) summer, and (d) autumn. Grid squares with trends statistically significant at the 5% level are marked with a dot. The units are degrees Celsius per 65 yr.

For 1900–2012, annual total precipitation has generally increased across southern Canada (Fig. 4c). The anomalies averaged over the region show a significant increase of 18% [14%–21%] during the 113-yr period (Fig. 4d). The rise in total precipitation results from a steady increase from the 1920s to the 1970s and a modest increase from the 1970s. The pattern of increasing trends is similar in all seasons (figures not presented). Seasonal positive trends are generally significant from coast to coast, with the exception of some areas in the central western (Alberta and Saskatchewan) and central eastern (eastern Ontario and southern Quebec) regions.

Trends in snowfall ratio reflect the combined effect of both precipitation and temperature. The annual trends are generally decreasing over 1948–2012 in many areas south of 65°N while they are increasing in the north (Fig. 6a). The snowfall ratio averaged over the country shows an increase from the beginning of the record to the 1970s, followed by a decrease to 2012 (Fig. 6b). The

peak snowfall ratio in the 1970s is consistent with North American winter snow cover extent, which reached twentieth-century maximum values around this time (Brown 2000). In winter, there is less evidence of change although significant decreasing trends are observed in the west (British Columbia) and east (southeastern Quebec) over the past 65 yr (figure not presented). The changes are more pronounced in spring and autumn. In spring, significant decreasing trends are found across western and central Canada (Fig. 7a). Since spring precipitation has not essentially changed in the past 65 yr over this area (Fig. 5b), the decreasing trends in snowfall ratio during spring is mainly due to the spring warming (Fig. 3b), which effectively decreased the proportion of snow. A similar connection is seen in autumn, where significant decreasing trends in northern Quebec (Fig. 7b) correspond to the autumn warming over the past 65 yr (Fig. 3d).

For 1900–2012, the annual snowfall ratio has generally increased in the northern part of southern Canada

FIG. 4. Trends in annual total precipitation for (a) 1948–2012 [$\% (65 \text{ yr})^{-1}$] and (c) 1900–2012 [$\% (113 \text{ yr})^{-1}$]. Grid squares with trends statistically significant at the 5% level are marked with a dot. Annual total precipitation anomalies for (b) Canada (1948–2012) and (d) southern Canada (1900–2012). The black line is an 11-yr running mean.

(north of 55°N) and decreased in several regions in the south (Fig. 6c). The snowfall ratio averaged over the region shows a steady increase from the 1920s to the 1970s, followed by a decrease to 2012 (Fig. 6d). Similar to the shorter period, there is less evidence of change in the winter snowfall ratio (not shown), except for some small areas of decreasing trends in the west (southern British Columbia) and east (southern Quebec). The changes in snowfall ratio during 1900–2012 are more pronounced in spring and autumn when increasing (decreasing) trends are found in the northern (southern) part of southern Canada. The increasing snowfall ratio trends north of 55°N are mainly due to increasing precipitation, whereas the decreasing trends in the south are largely due to the warming trends during the past 113 yr. Precipitation trends for 1948–2012 and 1900–2012 are generally in agreement with previous findings (Mekis and Vincent 2011; Zhang et al. 2000).

c. Trends in snow cover

Snow-cover duration has decreased in Canada and most of the decreasing trends are observed in spring. About 22% of the stations have significant decreasing trends in the first half of the snow year (Fig. 8a), whereas 43% of the stations have significant decreasing trends in the second half of the snow year (Fig. 8b). The SCD anomalies from the 1961–90 reference period averaged over the 104 stations show a significant decrease of 8 [3–14 days] and 10 days [5–15 days] during 1950–2012 for the first and second halves of the snow year. The trend toward earlier snow disappearance in the spring was previously documented by Brown and Braaten (1998) and is part of a hemispheric-wide trend of earlier melt of snow and ice (Lemke et al. 2007; Vaughan et al. 2013). Snow cover in North America was characterized by rapid decreases in the 1980s and early 1990s with a significant decreasing trend in April snow water equivalent for 1915–97 (Brown 2000).

FIG. 5. Trends in total precipitation for 1948–2012 for (a) winter, (b) spring, (c) summer, and (d) autumn. Grid squares with trends statistically significant at the 5% level are marked with a dot. The units are percentage per 65 yr.

The annual maximum snow depth shows a general tendency toward smaller values (Fig. 8c). A decrease of 4 cm [3–11 cm] during 1950–2012 is found when the anomalies are averaged over the 104 stations: of these, 23% exhibit a significant decrease of more than 20 cm. The decrease in the maximum snow depth in the southern regions is being driven by less winter precipitation (Fig. 5a) and a lower fraction of precipitation falling as snow from the winter warming (Fig. 3a). Significant trends toward earlier dates of maximum snow depth are observed at 26% of the stations (Fig. 8d). The data also indicate that, when averaged over the 104 stations, the annual maximum snow depth occurs earlier in the year by about 13 days [6–21 days]. These results are consistent with winter warming. They are also in agreement with broad-scale trends toward declining spring snowpack and earlier runoff over the northwestern United States (Mote 2006; Barnett et al. 2008).

d. Trends in streamflow

Evidence of significant change is mainly found in April mean streamflow and in the starting date of high-flow season over 1950–2012. The results show significant increasing trends in April mean streamflow at 25% of the sites (Fig. 9a) and significant decreasing trends in the starting date of the high-flow season at 21% of the sites (Fig. 9b), mostly located in the western and eastern parts of the country. The trends toward earlier high-flow season and increase in April mean streamflow were previously documented in Zhang et al. (2001) and are consistent with the trends found across western North America (Stewart et al. 2005; Brabets and Walvoord 2009). The earlier start of spring freshet and increasing streamflow in April may be attributed to a combination of several factors, including earlier spring snowmelt and an increased proportion of liquid precipitation, depending on location. However, they are also dependent

FIG. 6. Trends in annual snowfall ratio for (a) 1948–2012 [$\% (65 \text{ yr})^{-1}$] and (c) 1900–2012 [$\% (113 \text{ yr})^{-1}$]. Grid squares with trends statistically significant at the 5% level are marked with a dot. Annual snowfall ratio for (b) Canada (1948–2012) and (d) southern Canada (1900–2012). The black line is an 11-yr running mean.

on the maximum water storage of the snowpack and any changes in the distribution of the runoff. A recent study suggests that a shift in precipitation from snow toward rain does not necessarily lead to increasing streamflow overall (Berghuijs et al. 2014).

Analysis of the date of river ice breakup and freezeup indicate some evidence of trends toward earlier river ice breakup at most locations for 1950–2012 (Fig. 9c) and 1967–2012. There is less evidence of changes in the date of river ice freezeup (not shown). These results are consistent with previously published studies (Duguay et al. 2006; Latifovic and Pouliot 2007) that report widespread trends to earlier spring breakup with strong regional variability in freezeup dates. These trends are consistent with warmer spring temperature and earlier start of the spring freshet. They are also in agreement with the trends observed over shorter periods of time (Zhang et al. 2001; Bonsal et al. 2006).

5. Influence of large-scale oscillation indices on observed trends

a. Influence of the PDO and NAO indices on temperature trends

The regression coefficients associated with the PDO and NAO are first examined when the model is fitted for 1948–2012. The coefficients are significant for a higher number of grid points in winter and spring than in summer and autumn. Significant positive coefficients for PDO are found in the west (Figs. 10a,d), while significant negative coefficients for NAO are observed in the northeast (Figs. 10b,e). These results are consistent with those presented in previous studies (Liu et al. 2007; Wang et al. 2005; Bonsal et al. 2001), which showed positive correlation between surface air temperature and PDO in the west and negative correlation between surface air temperature and NAO in the northeast. The

FIG. 7. Trends in snowfall ratio for 1948–2012 for (a) spring and (b) autumn. Grid squares with trends statistically significant at the 5% level are marked with a dot. The units are percentage per 65 yr.

combination of the PDO and NAO indices explain about 21% (13%) of the variation in winter (spring) mean temperature in Canada during 1948–2012 (this percentage is calculated at each grid point and averaged

over the nation). This percentage is much smaller for summer and autumn.

When the trends in the residuals are assessed for 1948–2012, the winter and spring warming (Figs. 10c,f) is

FIG. 8. Trends in snow cover data for 1950–2012: snow-cover duration (number of days with snow on the ground ≥ 2 cm) during (a) the first half of the snow season (August–January) and (b) the second half of the snow season (February–July); (c) annual maximum snow depth; and (d) date of annual maximum snow depth. Upward (downward) pointing triangles indicate positive (negative) trends. Solid triangles correspond to trends significant at the 5% level.

FIG. 9. Trends in (a) April mean streamflow, (b) starting date of high-flow season, and (c) date of river ice breakup for 1950–2012. Upward (downward) pointing triangles indicate positive (negative) trends. Solid triangles correspond to trends significant at the 5% level.

less pronounced than the warming observed in the original data (Figs. 3a,b), mainly in the western and central regions. However, the trends are still significant in many regions and their magnitude is more consistent across the country. The winter (spring) time series of the residuals averaged over the nation indicate a significant warming of 2.1°C (1.0°C) over the past 65 yr while the original winter (spring) data show a significant increase of 3.3°C (1.8°C). These results demonstrate that, while the oscillations explain some of the temperature variations over 1948–2012, the observed trends cannot be

explained by low-frequency variability modes alone since there is still significant warming after removing the effects of the PDO and NAO indices. The summer and autumn trends are basically the same before and after removing the influence of the oscillations.

For 1900–2012, significant positive coefficients for PDO are found in the southwest, whereas significant negative coefficients for NAO are observed over a small area in the southeast, during winter and spring (figures not presented). The PDO and NAO indices explain only 16% (10%) of the variation in winter (spring) mean

FIG. 10. Regression coefficients for (a) PDO and (b) NAO when the model is fitted to winter mean temperature. (c) Trends in winter mean temperature for 1948–2012 after removing the influence of PDO and NAO. Regression coefficients for (d) PDO and (e) NAO when the model is fitted to spring mean temperature. (f) Trends in spring mean temperature for 1948–2012 after removing the influence of PDO and NAO. Grid squares with trends (or coefficients) statistically significant at the 5% level are marked with a dot. The units are degrees Celsius per 65 yr.

temperature in southern Canada during 1900–2012. The temperature trends after removing the influence of the PDO and NAO indices are almost identical to those observed in the original data (Fig. 2c). The winter (spring) time series of the residuals averaged over the southern Canada indicate a significant warming of 2.5°C (1.8°C) over the past 113 yr, while the original winter (spring) data show a significant increase of 2.6°C (1.9°C). The results indicate that the influence of the PDO and NAO oscillations on the observed temperature trends is very small in southern Canada over the past 113 yr. They also suggest that the magnitude of the trends is more similar over both periods of time after removing the influence of the oscillations. In particular, the winter mean temperature has increased by 2.1°C in Canada for 1948–2012 while it has increased by 2.5°C in southern Canada for 1900–2012 after removing the effects of the oscillations (although the area covered is different).

b. Influence of NPI and NAO (or PDO and AMO) on temperature trends

Annual and seasonal mean temperature trends are also examined after removing the influence of the atmospheric (NPI and NAO) and oceanic (PDO and AMO) oscillations separately. The resulting trends for 1948–2012 and 1900–2012 are similar to those obtained when the effects of the PDO and NAO are taken into account. In winter and spring, significant negative coefficients for NPI are mainly found in the western and central regions and significant negative coefficients for NAO prevail in the northeast (figures not presented). For the same seasons, significant positive coefficients for AMO are found in the central and eastern regions whereas significant positive coefficients for PDO prevail in the west. The 1948–2012 trends in winter and spring mean temperatures after removing the effects of NPI and NAO (PDO and AMO) are very similar to those presented in Figs. 10c,f. Overall, these results indicate that the warming is still significant and more consistent across the country after removing the influence of the large-scale oscillations. They also suggest that the observed temperature trends cannot be explained by low-frequency variability modes alone.

c. Influence of PDO and NAO on the trends in other climate elements

Annual and seasonal total precipitation and snowfall ratio trends are assessed after removing the influence of the PDO and NAO indices. The combination of the PDO and NAO explain less than 10% of the variation in these two elements for 1948–2012 and 1900–2012. The regression coefficients are significant for a greater number of grid points for winter precipitation and spring

snowfall ratio during 1948–2012. For winter precipitation, significant negative coefficients for PDO are found in the south (Fig. 11a) and significant negative coefficients for NAO are found in the northeast (Fig. 11b). The trends in winter precipitation for 1948–2012 after removing the effect of the oscillations (Fig. 11c) are similar to those obtained from the original data (Fig. 5a) with the exception of weaker decreasing trends in the southwest. For spring snowfall ratio, significant negative coefficients for PDO prevail in the west (Fig. 11d), whereas coefficients for NAO are generally near zero (Fig. 11e). The trends in spring snowfall ratio for 1948–2012 after removing the influence of PDO and NAO (Fig. 11f) are similar to those obtained from the original data (Fig. 7a), with the exception of less extensive decreasing trends in the west. The results indicate that, while the PDO index explains some of the variations in winter precipitation and spring precipitation falling as snow during 1948–2012, the magnitude and significance of the trends do not change very much after removing the influence of the PDO and NAO for 1948–2012. There is no evidence of the PDO and NAO impact on the precipitation and snowfall ratio trends during 1900–2012.

When the trends are assessed for various snow-cover and streamflow indices, the regression coefficients associated with the PDO and NAO are significant at a few stations only. The trends after removing the effects of PDO and NAO are almost identical to those obtained from the original values (Figs. 8 and 9). There is no evidence that the PDO and NAO are affecting the trends in the snow-cover and streamflow indices by very much during 1950–2012 (although the number of stations used in this study is limited).

6. Summary and discussion

The trend results reported in this study present a picture of a changing climate in Canada which is consistent across multiple climate elements. Over the past six decades, surface air temperature has increased in Canada, with the largest warming occurring in winter and spring. Precipitation totals have increased principally in the north in all seasons. Winter precipitation has decreased in the southwest and there have been widespread decreases in the amount of precipitation falling as snow in the south. These changes in temperature and precipitation have led to a shorter snow-cover season, mainly in response to earlier snowmelt (in all regions) and lower snowfall amounts (in southern regions). A shorter snow accumulation period and reduced snowfall amounts has resulted in a decrease in annual maximum snow accumulations and earlier dates of maximum snow

FIG. 11. Regression coefficients for (a) PDO and (b) NAO when the model is fitted to winter precipitation. (c) Trends in winter precipitation for 1948–2012 after removing the influence of PDO and NAO. Regression coefficients for (d) PDO and (e) NAO when the model is fitted to spring snowfall ratio. (f) Trends in spring snowfall ratio for 1948–2012 after removing the influence of PDO and NAO. Grid squares with trends (or coefficients) statistically significant at the 5% level are marked with a dot. The units are percentage per 65 yr.

depth at many stations. An observed earlier start of spring freshet and increasing streamflow in April are consistent with earlier spring snowmelt because of winter and spring warming. Over the past century, temperature has increased in southern Canada, but the rate of increase was not consistent and included a modest cooling during 1940–70. During the same period, the precipitation has increased almost everywhere across the region and the amount of precipitation falling as snow has increased north of 55°N and decreased in the south.

When the influence of large-scale oscillations is taken into account, the warming observed in Canada during 1948–2012 is slightly reduced in the western regions, especially during winter and spring, but the temperature trends are still significant and the warming is more consistent across the country. There are less decreasing trends in winter precipitation totals and spring precipitation falling as snow during 1948–2012 in the southwest after removing the effects of the oscillations, but the overall pattern of increasing winter precipitation trends in the north and decreasing spring snowfall ratio trends in the south remains the same. There is no evidence that the large-scale oscillations have influenced the temperature and precipitation trends over 1900–2012 and the snow-cover and streamflow indices trends

over 1950–2012. These results clearly demonstrate that, while the oscillations explain some of the climate variations during 1948–2012, the observed temperature and precipitation trends cannot be explained by low-frequency variability modes alone. Other factors, external to the climate system, such as increase in greenhouse gases and aerosols in the atmosphere may have played a significant role in the observed changes in climate (Wan et al. 2015; Gillett et al. 2008; Min et al. 2008a; Zhang et al. 2006). Ongoing work involves the comparison of the changes observed in historical data with those simulated by climate models under various external forcing and the results will be reported in a different study.

This study presents an analysis of trends in several climate elements using the best updated data available over similar periods of time in order to highlight the consistencies among the trends in related climate variables. It is important to closely monitor climate change in order to improve our understanding regarding the various mechanisms responsible for climate variations. Canada's climate shows multidecadal-scale variability over the past century associated with low-frequency atmospheric and oceanic oscillations. This study reports, for the first time, climate trends in Canada after removing potential mechanisms representing low-frequency

variations. The results show that large-scale atmospheric and oceanic oscillations have influenced regional climate trends to some extent. However, it also reveals that these indices alone do not explain long-term changes observed in various climate elements in Canada.

Acknowledgments. The authors thank Emma Watson and Bin Yu from the Climate Research Division of the Sciences and Technologies Branch of Environment Canada and three anonymous reviewers for their helpful comments and suggestions that have helped to improve the manuscript.

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F.3 Correspondence with Environment Canada Access to Information advisor regarding missing email attachment

Below is an email exchange between Access to Information requester Joseph Hickey and Environment Canada Access to Information Advisor Martine Mainville regarding an email attachment that was not provided in Environment Canada's release of emails.

Environment Canada subsequently provided the missing attachment, which is included in Appendix F.4 of this report.

Joseph Hickey <jhick059@gmail.com>

Completed Access to Information request A-2022-00711

Mainville, Martine (elle, la | she, her) (ECCC) <Martine.Mainville@ec.gc.ca>
To: Joseph Hickey <jhick059@gmail.com>

Wed, May 17, 2023 at 2:10 PM

Good afternoon Mr. Hickey,

Please find attached, the missing attachment that you are referring to in your email below.

Kind regards,

Martine Mainville (she/her/elle)

Conseillère principale AIPRP

Accès à l'information et protection des renseignements personnels / Secrétariat Ministériel

Environnement et Changement climatique Canada / Gouvernement du Canada

martine.mainville@ec.gc.ca

Senior ATIP Advisor

Access to Information and Privacy / Corporate Secretariat

Environment and Climate Change Canada / Government of Canada

martine.mainville@ec.gc.ca

Government
of Canada

Gouvernement
du Canada

Canada

From: Joseph Hickey <jhick059@gmail.com>

Sent: Thursday, May 11, 2023 12:12 PM

To: Mainville, Martine (elle, la | she, her) (ECCC) <Martine.Mainville@ec.gc.ca>

Subject: Re: Completed Access to Information request A-2022-00711

Dear Ms. Mainville,

I received your response to my access request A-2022-00711 on March 21, 2023. Your response was communicated to me via your email below, which had in attachment a response letter (filename "A-2022-00711 - Response Letter.pdf") and a PDF file containing the released records (filename "A-2022-00711 - Release.pdf").

Page 3 of the file "A-2022-00711 - Release.pdf" contains an email sent on December 9, 2020 at 5:46 PM from Julien McDonald-Guimond <JMcDonald-Guimond@bank-banque-canada.ca> to DCCAH / AHCCD (EC) <ec.dccah-ahccd.ec@canada.ca> with Vincent, Lucie (EC) <lucie.vincent@canada.ca> in Cc. The email has the Subject "RE: Inquiry on AHCCD daily data".

The email reads as follows:

"Hi Megan,

Thank you very much for your help. You can find attached a table with all instances of Tmin > Tmax that I've found in the AHCCD daily data.

All the best,

Julien"

The email quoted above refers to an "attached table with all instances of Tmin > Tmax". However, no such attachment was included in the release (file "A-2022-00711 - Release.pdf") that was sent to me.

Please send me the table referred to in Mr. McDonald-Guimond's email of December 9, 2020. I note that my access request A-2022-00711 (submitted on July 5, 2022) covers all attachments to the respondent emails.

Please respond to my instant request for the missing attachment(s) by no later than May 17, 2023.

Please confirm receipt of this email.

Sincerely,
Joseph Hickey

On Tue, Mar 21, 2023 at 3:15 PM Mainville,Martine (elle, la | she, her) (ECCC) <Martine.Mainville@ec.gc.ca> wrote:

Good afternoon,

Please find attached the complete response to your request under the *Access to Information Act*.

If you have any questions, please feel free to contact me.

Thank you,

Martine Mainville (she/her/elle)

Conseillère principale AIPRP

Accès à l'information et protection des renseignements personnels / Secrétariat Ministériel

Environnement et Changement climatique Canada / Gouvernement du Canada

martine.mainville@ec.gc.ca

F.4 Missing email attachment: Table of instances for which daily minimum temperature was greater than daily maximum temperature, for the 2nd generation of the AHCCD

Below is the email attachment that was missing from Environment Canada's initial release of documents pursuant to the Access to Information request.

The attachment consists of a table (299 pages) sent to Environment Canada researchers by Bank of Canada Economist Julien McDonald-Guimond containing 10,159 cases in which the daily minimum temperature in the 2nd generation of the AHCCD was greater than the daily maximum temperature for the same AHCCD station, as described in section 3.3 of the main text.

	time	stn_name	prov	stn_id	cmalon	cmalat	elev	max_temp	min_temp	diff	problem
1	1976-12-31	GOOSE	NFLD	8501900	-60.42	53.32	49	-17.8	-2.7	-15.1	1
2	1971-03-03	YELLOWKNIFE	NWT	2204101	-114.43	62.47	206	-26.7	-25.5	-1.2	1
3	1885-01-12	CALGARY	ALTA	3031092	-114.02	51.12	1099	-30.9	-30	-0.9	1
4	1886-01-14	CALGARY	ALTA	3031092	-114.02	51.12	1099	-22.5	-22.4	-0.1	1
5	1886-12-24	CALGARY	ALTA	3031092	-114.02	51.12	1099	-23.6	-22.4	-1.2	1
6	1887-02-13	CALGARY	ALTA	3031092	-114.02	51.12	1099	-17.6	-17.3	-0.3	1
7	1887-12-29	CALGARY	ALTA	3031092	-114.02	51.12	1099	-24.1	-23.4	-0.7	1
8	1887-12-30	CALGARY	ALTA	3031092	-114.02	51.12	1099	-25.3	-24.6	-0.7	1
9	1888-01-18	CALGARY	ALTA	3031092	-114.02	51.12	1099	-30.3	-30	-0.3	1
10	1888-10-23	CALGARY	ALTA	3031092	-114.02	51.12	1099	0.4	0.8	-0.4	1
11	1889-01-18	CALGARY	ALTA	3031092	-114.02	51.12	1099	-18.9	-18.7	-0.2	1
12	1889-02-15	CALGARY	ALTA	3031092	-114.02	51.12	1099	-20	-19.8	-0.2	1
13	1891-02-13	CALGARY	ALTA	3031092	-114.02	51.12	1099	-24.2	-21.9	-2.3	1
14	1892-01-17	CALGARY	ALTA	3031092	-114.02	51.12	1099	-24.8	-24.6	-0.2	1
15	1892-12-25	CALGARY	ALTA	3031092	-114.02	51.12	1099	-28.1	-27.9	-0.2	1
16	1893-02-12	CALGARY	ALTA	3031092	-114.02	51.12	1099	-19.5	-19.2	-0.3	1
17	1895-01-04	CALGARY	ALTA	3031092	-114.02	51.12	1099	-20.7	-20.3	-0.4	1
18	1896-01-16	CALGARY	ALTA	3031092	-114.02	51.12	1099	-34.8	-34	-0.8	1
19	1896-11-15	CALGARY	ALTA	3031092	-114.02	51.12	1099	-18.9	-18.7	-0.2	1
20	1896-11-30	CALGARY	ALTA	3031092	-114.02	51.12	1099	-23	-22.4	-0.6	1
21	1900-11-17	CALGARY	ALTA	3031092	-114.02	51.12	1099	-21.9	-21.3	-0.6	1
22	1902-05-18	CALGARY	ALTA	3031092	-114.02	51.12	1099	5.3	5.9	-0.6	1
23	1903-03-08	CALGARY	ALTA	3031092	-114.02	51.12	1099	-17.6	-17.3	-0.3	1
24	1904-02-06	CALGARY	ALTA	3031092	-114.02	51.12	1099	-25.3	-24.6	-0.7	1
25	1904-02-07	CALGARY	ALTA	3031092	-114.02	51.12	1099	-25.3	-25.1	-0.2	1
26	1904-02-20	CALGARY	ALTA	3031092	-114.02	51.12	1099	-23	-22.4	-0.6	1
27	1906-01-22	CALGARY	ALTA	3031092	-114.02	51.12	1099	-30.3	-30	-0.3	1
28	1906-12-07	CALGARY	ALTA	3031092	-114.02	51.12	1099	-24.8	-23.4	-1.4	1
29	1907-01-04	CALGARY	ALTA	3031092	-114.02	51.12	1099	-26.4	-25.7	-0.7	1
30	1908-10-02	CALGARY	ALTA	3031092	-114.02	51.12	1099	2.3	2.6	-0.3	1
31	1908-12-30	CALGARY	ALTA	3031092	-114.02	51.12	1099	-24.2	-24	-0.2	1
32	1910-02-14	CALGARY	ALTA	3031092	-114.02	51.12	1099	-19.5	-18.7	-0.8	1
33	1910-02-20	CALGARY	ALTA	3031092	-114.02	51.12	1099	-23.6	-23.4	-0.2	1

34	1910-12-31	CALGARY	ALTA	3031092	-114.02	51.12	1099	-25.3	-24	-1.3	1
35	1911-01-09	CALGARY	ALTA	3031092	-114.02	51.12	1099	-32	-30.6	-1.4	1
36	1911-01-10	CALGARY	ALTA	3031092	-114.02	51.12	1099	-35.9	-34	-1.9	1
37	1911-01-11	CALGARY	ALTA	3031092	-114.02	51.12	1099	-36.4	-35	-1.4	1
38	1911-01-25	CALGARY	ALTA	3031092	-114.02	51.12	1099	-28.7	-27.9	-0.8	1
39	1911-01-31	CALGARY	ALTA	3031092	-114.02	51.12	1099	-23	-21.9	-1.1	1
40	1911-02-01	CALGARY	ALTA	3031092	-114.02	51.12	1099	-28.1	-27.3	-0.8	1
41	1911-06-07	CALGARY	ALTA	3031092	-114.02	51.12	1099	5.9	6.4	-0.5	1
42	1911-06-24	CALGARY	ALTA	3031092	-114.02	51.12	1099	12.5	12.6	-0.1	1
43	1911-10-23	CALGARY	ALTA	3031092	-114.02	51.12	1099	1	1.4	-0.4	1
44	1911-11-08	CALGARY	ALTA	3031092	-114.02	51.12	1099	-17.6	-17.2	-0.4	1
45	1911-11-09	CALGARY	ALTA	3031092	-114.02	51.12	1099	-23	-22.4	-0.6	1
46	1911-12-29	CALGARY	ALTA	3031092	-114.02	51.12	1099	-31.4	-31.1	-0.3	1
47	1912-01-02	CALGARY	ALTA	3031092	-114.02	51.12	1099	-20.7	-20.3	-0.4	1
48	1912-01-09	CALGARY	ALTA	3031092	-114.02	51.12	1099	-28.1	-27.9	-0.2	1
49	1913-01-15	CALGARY	ALTA	3031092	-114.02	51.12	1099	-25	-24.6	-0.4	1
50	1913-03-18	CALGARY	ALTA	3031092	-114.02	51.12	1099	-19.5	-19.3	-0.2	1
51	1913-05-08	CALGARY	ALTA	3031092	-114.02	51.12	1099	-0.6	1.4	-2	1
52	1914-10-04	CALGARY	ALTA	3031092	-114.02	51.12	1099	-0.1	0	-0.1	1
53	1914-10-05	CALGARY	ALTA	3031092	-114.02	51.12	1099	-0.6	0.8	-1.4	1
54	1914-10-11	CALGARY	ALTA	3031092	-114.02	51.12	1099	-0.6	0	-0.6	1
55	1914-12-06	CALGARY	ALTA	3031092	-114.02	51.12	1099	-17.8	-17.7	-0.1	1
56	1915-05-15	CALGARY	ALTA	3031092	-114.02	51.12	1099	-0.6	0	-0.6	1
57	1916-01-22	CALGARY	ALTA	3031092	-114.02	51.12	1099	-31.1	-29.5	-1.6	1
58	1916-08-18	CALGARY	ALTA	3031092	-114.02	51.12	1099	8.3	8.6	-0.3	1
59	1916-12-25	CALGARY	ALTA	3031092	-114.02	51.12	1099	-26.1	-25.7	-0.4	1
60	1917-01-29	CALGARY	ALTA	3031092	-114.02	51.12	1099	-31.7	-31.1	-0.6	1
61	1917-09-08	CALGARY	ALTA	3031092	-114.02	51.12	1099	4	4.7	-0.7	1
62	1917-12-10	CALGARY	ALTA	3031092	-114.02	51.12	1099	-23.4	-22.4	-1	1
63	1917-12-26	CALGARY	ALTA	3031092	-114.02	51.12	1099	-31.7	-30.6	-1.1	1
64	1917-12-27	CALGARY	ALTA	3031092	-114.02	51.12	1099	-31.7	-29.5	-2.2	1
65	1921-01-28	CALGARY	ALTA	3031092	-114.02	51.12	1099	-13.8	-13.3	-0.5	1
66	1921-11-23	CALGARY	ALTA	3031092	-114.02	51.12	1099	-23.9	-23	-0.9	1
67	1921-11-24	CALGARY	ALTA	3031092	-114.02	51.12	1099	-22.8	-22.4	-0.4	1

68	1923-06-22	CALGARY	ALTA	3031092	-114.02	51.12	1099	6.3	6.4	-0.1	1
69	1926-02-11	CALGARY	ALTA	3031092	-114.02	51.12	1099	0	0.1	-0.1	1
70	1926-08-19	CALGARY	ALTA	3031092	-114.02	51.12	1099	10.9	11.5	-0.6	1
71	1930-09-07	CALGARY	ALTA	3031092	-114.02	51.12	1099	10.5	10.9	-0.4	1
72	1930-11-25	CALGARY	ALTA	3031092	-114.02	51.12	1099	0	0.1	-0.1	1
73	1932-04-24	CALGARY	ALTA	3031092	-114.02	51.12	1099	2.2	2.6	-0.4	1
74	1932-10-06	CALGARY	ALTA	3031092	-114.02	51.12	1099	0	0.1	-0.1	1
75	1937-01-27	CALGARY	ALTA	3031092	-114.02	51.12	1099	-25.6	-24.6	-1	1
76	1938-02-01	CALGARY	ALTA	3031092	-114.02	51.12	1099	-20	-19.3	-0.7	1
77	1939-02-07	CALGARY	ALTA	3031092	-114.02	51.12	1099	-32.2	-31.8	-0.4	1
78	1967-12-31	GERALDTON	ONT	6042716	-86.93	49.78	348	-30.7	-30.6	-0.1	1
79	1969-01-10	GERALDTON	ONT	6042716	-86.93	49.78	348	-19.5	-19.4	-0.1	1
80	1990-11-12	TIMMINS	ONT	6078286	-81.38	48.57	295	-7.2	-6.2	-1	1
81	2018-03-25	TORONTO	ONT	6158355	-79.4	43.67	113	2.5	3	-0.5	1
82	2017-11-10	WINDSOR	ONT	6139527	-82.97	42.27	190	-1.4	-0.5	-0.9	1
83	2017-11-23	WINDSOR	ONT	6139527	-82.97	42.27	190	4	6.2	-2.2	1
84	2018-09-22	WINDSOR	ONT	6139527	-82.97	42.27	190	16.1	18.9	-2.8	1
85	1989-11-10	SMITHERS	BC	1077500	-127.18	54.82	522	-3.8	-2	-1.8	1
86	1999-02-16	SMITHERS	BC	1077500	-127.18	54.82	522	-4	-3.3	-0.7	1
87	1909-08-22	SWIFT CURRENT	SASK	4028038	-107.73	50.27	817	27	27.8	-0.8	1
88	1927-05-21	SWIFT CURRENT	SASK	4028038	-107.73	50.27	817	5.2	5.6	-0.4	1
89	1937-09-29	SWIFT CURRENT	SASK	4028038	-107.73	50.27	817	1.6	1.7	-0.1	1
90	1937-10-16	SWIFT CURRENT	SASK	4028038	-107.73	50.27	817	13.3	13.9	-0.6	1
91	1976-01-03	KAPUSKASING	ONT	6073976	-82.47	49.42	227	-25.6	-18.8	-6.8	1
92	2010-07-10	LANGARA	BC	1054500	-133.05	54.25	43	13.8	18.8	-5	1
93	2012-08-27	LANGARA	BC	1054500	-133.05	54.25	43	10.6	11.4	-0.8	1
94	2016-12-10	LANGARA	BC	1054500	-133.05	54.25	43	0	1.5	-1.5	1
95	2018-10-23	RESOLUTE	NU	2403498	-94.98	74.72	68	-19.5	-18.6	-0.9	1
96	1994-12-22	WINNIPEG	MAN	502S001	-97.23	49.92	239	1.4	7.9	-6.5	1
97	1995-07-18	THUNDER BAY	ONT	6048260	-89.33	48.37	199	14.1	15.5	-1.4	1
98	1997-03-22	THUNDER BAY	ONT	6048260	-89.33	48.37	199	-3.9	-2.8	-1.1	1
99	1963-02-16	KUUJJUAQ	QUE	7113535	-68.42	58.1	40	-33.9	-32.7	-1.2	1
100	2005-01-05	KUUJJUAQ	QUE	7113535	-68.42	58.1	40	-35.2	-33.6	-1.6	1
101	1945-11-20	SEPT-ILES	QUE	7047914	-66.27	50.22	53	-3	-2.2	-0.8	1

102	1948-11-29	SEPT-ILES	QUE	7047914	-66.27	50.22	53	-5.3	-5	-0.3	1
103	1951-04-13	SEPT-ILES	QUE	7047914	-66.27	50.22	53	-0.4	0	-0.4	1
104	1994-12-06	YARMOUTH	NS	8206495	-66.08	43.83	43	3.9	4.5	-0.6	1
105	2018-12-27	YARMOUTH	NS	8206495	-66.08	43.83	43	-3.3	2	-5.3	1
106	1913-11-28	SHAWNIGAN LAKE	BC	1017230	-123.63	48.65	159	4.8	5.1	-0.3	1
107	1914-06-07	SHAWNIGAN LAKE	BC	1017230	-123.63	48.65	159	9.7	9.8	-0.1	1
108	1915-12-20	SHAWNIGAN LAKE	BC	1017230	-123.63	48.65	159	4.8	5	-0.2	1
109	1915-12-31	SHAWNIGAN LAKE	BC	1017230	-123.63	48.65	159	-2	-1.9	-0.1	1
110	1916-02-03	SHAWNIGAN LAKE	BC	1017230	-123.63	48.65	159	-1.5	-1.3	-0.2	1
111	1918-01-11	SHAWNIGAN LAKE	BC	1017230	-123.63	48.65	159	1.4	1.7	-0.3	1
112	1918-01-20	SHAWNIGAN LAKE	BC	1017230	-123.63	48.65	159	2.5	2.8	-0.3	1
113	1919-11-18	SHAWNIGAN LAKE	BC	1017230	-123.63	48.65	159	10.1	10.4	-0.3	1
114	1921-11-10	SHAWNIGAN LAKE	BC	1017230	-123.63	48.65	159	9.2	9.4	-0.2	1
115	1921-12-18	SHAWNIGAN LAKE	BC	1017230	-123.63	48.65	159	-5.3	-4.2	-1.1	1
116	1922-12-05	SHAWNIGAN LAKE	BC	1017230	-123.63	48.65	159	-2.5	-1.3	-1.2	1
117	1923-01-07	SHAWNIGAN LAKE	BC	1017230	-123.63	48.65	159	5.9	6.2	-0.3	1
118	1923-12-30	SHAWNIGAN LAKE	BC	1017230	-123.63	48.65	159	-7.1	-7	-0.1	1
119	1924-04-10	SHAWNIGAN LAKE	BC	1017230	-123.63	48.65	159	7	7.2	-0.2	1
120	1925-10-27	SHAWNIGAN LAKE	BC	1017230	-123.63	48.65	159	6.5	6.7	-0.2	1
121	1927-10-03	SHAWNIGAN LAKE	BC	1017230	-123.63	48.65	159	4.8	6.2	-1.4	1
122	1927-12-29	SHAWNIGAN LAKE	BC	1017230	-123.63	48.65	159	-7.1	-7	-0.1	1
123	1928-12-17	SHAWNIGAN LAKE	BC	1017230	-123.63	48.65	159	3	3.2	-0.2	1
124	1929-11-16	SHAWNIGAN LAKE	BC	1017230	-123.63	48.65	159	6.5	7.3	-0.8	1
125	1930-01-05	SHAWNIGAN LAKE	BC	1017230	-123.63	48.65	159	-0.9	-0.8	-0.1	1
126	1931-06-16	SHAWNIGAN LAKE	BC	1017230	-123.63	48.65	159	12.4	13.1	-0.7	1
127	1931-11-06	SHAWNIGAN LAKE	BC	1017230	-123.63	48.65	159	7.6	7.9	-0.3	1
128	1932-01-30	SHAWNIGAN LAKE	BC	1017230	-123.63	48.65	159	-5.3	-4.8	-0.5	1
129	1934-10-24	SHAWNIGAN LAKE	BC	1017230	-123.63	48.65	159	7.6	7.9	-0.3	1
130	1934-11-04	SHAWNIGAN LAKE	BC	1017230	-123.63	48.65	159	7	7.2	-0.2	1
131	1934-12-13	SHAWNIGAN LAKE	BC	1017230	-123.63	48.65	159	6.5	6.7	-0.2	1
132	1935-11-26	SHAWNIGAN LAKE	BC	1017230	-123.63	48.65	159	9.7	9.9	-0.2	1
133	1935-11-30	SHAWNIGAN LAKE	BC	1017230	-123.63	48.65	159	8.7	9	-0.3	1
134	1936-01-09	SHAWNIGAN LAKE	BC	1017230	-123.63	48.65	159	5.4	5.6	-0.2	1
135	1936-01-21	SHAWNIGAN LAKE	BC	1017230	-123.63	48.65	159	5.9	7.2	-1.3	1

136	1936-02-12	SHAWNIGAN LAKE	BC	1017230	-123.63	48.65	159	-1.5	-1.3	-0.2	1
137	1937-11-19	SHAWNIGAN LAKE	BC	1017230	-123.63	48.65	159	4.8	5	-0.2	1
138	1937-11-28	SHAWNIGAN LAKE	BC	1017230	-123.63	48.65	159	4.2	4.4	-0.2	1
139	1938-01-31	SHAWNIGAN LAKE	BC	1017230	-123.63	48.65	159	-1.5	-1.3	-0.2	1
140	1939-12-01	SHAWNIGAN LAKE	BC	1017230	-123.63	48.65	159	6.5	6.7	-0.2	1
141	1940-11-28	SHAWNIGAN LAKE	BC	1017230	-123.63	48.65	159	8.1	8.5	-0.4	1
142	1940-11-30	SHAWNIGAN LAKE	BC	1017230	-123.63	48.65	159	7.6	8.5	-0.9	1
143	1940-12-29	SHAWNIGAN LAKE	BC	1017230	-123.63	48.65	159	4.2	5.1	-0.9	1
144	1945-02-11	SHAWNIGAN LAKE	BC	1017230	-123.63	48.65	159	10.1	10.4	-0.3	1
145	1946-03-26	SHAWNIGAN LAKE	BC	1017230	-123.63	48.65	159	5.9	7.2	-1.3	1
146	1948-11-14	SHAWNIGAN LAKE	BC	1017230	-123.63	48.65	159	6.5	6.7	-0.2	1
147	1948-11-16	SHAWNIGAN LAKE	BC	1017230	-123.63	48.65	159	5.9	6.1	-0.2	1
148	1949-07-22	SHAWNIGAN LAKE	BC	1017230	-123.63	48.65	159	15.1	15.3	-0.2	1
149	1950-10-19	SHAWNIGAN LAKE	BC	1017230	-123.63	48.65	159	9.1	9.8	-0.7	1
150	1952-01-15	SHAWNIGAN LAKE	BC	1017230	-123.63	48.65	159	0.8	1	-0.2	1
151	1955-01-01	SHAWNIGAN LAKE	BC	1017230	-123.63	48.65	159	4.8	5.6	-0.8	1
152	1955-02-07	SHAWNIGAN LAKE	BC	1017230	-123.63	48.65	159	3.7	5	-1.3	1
153	1955-02-25	SHAWNIGAN LAKE	BC	1017230	-123.63	48.65	159	0.8	2.3	-1.5	1
154	1957-01-11	SHAWNIGAN LAKE	BC	1017230	-123.63	48.65	159	0.3	0.8	-0.5	1
155	1904-01-18	VERNON	BC	1128582	-119.2	50.23	482	-8.1	-8	-0.1	1
156	1906-11-13	VERNON	BC	1128582	-119.2	50.23	482	5.4	5.5	-0.1	1
157	1906-12-31	VERNON	BC	1128582	-119.2	50.23	482	-13.1	-12.3	-0.8	1
158	1907-08-26	VERNON	BC	1128582	-119.2	50.23	482	13.1	13.4	-0.3	1
159	1909-01-04	VERNON	BC	1128582	-119.2	50.23	482	-14.8	-14	-0.8	1
160	1909-09-30	VERNON	BC	1128582	-119.2	50.23	482	10.3	10.5	-0.2	1
161	1911-01-12	VERNON	BC	1128582	-119.2	50.23	482	-24.1	-24	-0.1	1
162	1911-11-19	VERNON	BC	1128582	-119.2	50.23	482	1.6	1.7	-0.1	1
163	1911-12-28	VERNON	BC	1128582	-119.2	50.23	482	-6.9	-6.5	-0.4	1
164	1912-01-10	VERNON	BC	1128582	-119.2	50.23	482	-13.6	-13.4	-0.2	1
165	1914-10-11	VERNON	BC	1128582	-119.2	50.23	482	8.7	8.9	-0.2	1
166	1916-01-10	VERNON	BC	1128582	-119.2	50.23	482	-22	-20.6	-1.4	1
167	1916-12-28	VERNON	BC	1128582	-119.2	50.23	482	-13.6	-13.4	-0.2	1
168	1920-01-18	VERNON	BC	1128582	-119.2	50.23	482	7.2	7.4	-0.2	1
169	1921-10-26	VERNON	BC	1128582	-119.2	50.23	482	6.1	6.9	-0.8	1

170	1921-12-18	VERNON	BC	1128582	-119.2	50.23	482	-9.8	-9.1	-0.7	1
171	1922-01-29	VERNON	BC	1128582	-119.2	50.23	482	-8.1	-8	-0.1	1
172	1922-10-04	VERNON	BC	1128582	-119.2	50.23	482	9.3	10	-0.7	1
173	1922-10-27	VERNON	BC	1128582	-119.2	50.23	482	7.7	8.3	-0.6	1
174	1922-12-10	VERNON	BC	1128582	-119.2	50.23	482	-13.6	-12.8	-0.8	1
175	1924-12-15	VERNON	BC	1128582	-119.2	50.23	482	-14.1	-13.4	-0.7	1
176	1926-12-12	VERNON	BC	1128582	-119.2	50.23	482	-7.6	-7.5	-0.1	1
177	1927-01-17	VERNON	BC	1128582	-119.2	50.23	482	-0.5	-0.3	-0.2	1
178	1927-01-18	VERNON	BC	1128582	-119.2	50.23	482	-13.1	-12.8	-0.3	1
179	1927-11-25	VERNON	BC	1128582	-119.2	50.23	482	3.4	4.2	-0.8	1
180	1927-12-05	VERNON	BC	1128582	-119.2	50.23	482	1.1	1.6	-0.5	1
181	1927-12-09	VERNON	BC	1128582	-119.2	50.23	482	-14.1	-13.4	-0.7	1
182	1927-12-28	VERNON	BC	1128582	-119.2	50.23	482	-9.8	-8.6	-1.2	1
183	1929-01-21	VERNON	BC	1128582	-119.2	50.23	482	-13.6	-12.3	-1.3	1
184	1929-11-16	VERNON	BC	1128582	-119.2	50.23	482	1.6	1.7	-0.1	1
185	1929-12-09	VERNON	BC	1128582	-119.2	50.23	482	-8.1	-8	-0.1	1
186	1929-12-10	VERNON	BC	1128582	-119.2	50.23	482	-10.4	-10.2	-0.2	1
187	1930-01-05	VERNON	BC	1128582	-119.2	50.23	482	-13.6	-13.4	-0.2	1
188	1930-03-19	VERNON	BC	1128582	-119.2	50.23	482	8.2	8.3	-0.1	1
189	1930-10-26	VERNON	BC	1128582	-119.2	50.23	482	4.1	4.2	-0.1	1
190	1930-11-11	VERNON	BC	1128582	-119.2	50.23	482	7.2	7.9	-0.7	1
191	1930-11-13	VERNON	BC	1128582	-119.2	50.23	482	0.1	0.5	-0.4	1
192	1930-11-14	VERNON	BC	1128582	-119.2	50.23	482	-1.5	-1.2	-0.3	1
193	1931-01-27	VERNON	BC	1128582	-119.2	50.23	482	1.6	1.7	-0.1	1
194	1932-03-02	VERNON	BC	1128582	-119.2	50.23	482	-1.5	-0.7	-0.8	1
195	1933-01-16	VERNON	BC	1128582	-119.2	50.23	482	-8.1	-8	-0.1	1
196	1933-12-11	VERNON	BC	1128582	-119.2	50.23	482	-3.1	-3	-0.1	1
197	1934-08-02	VERNON	BC	1128582	-119.2	50.23	482	17.9	18	-0.1	1
198	1935-01-13	VERNON	BC	1128582	-119.2	50.23	482	-11.4	-11.3	-0.1	1
199	1935-10-28	VERNON	BC	1128582	-119.2	50.23	482	-0.5	0	-0.5	1
200	1935-11-27	VERNON	BC	1128582	-119.2	50.23	482	1.6	1.7	-0.1	1
201	1936-12-27	VERNON	BC	1128582	-119.2	50.23	482	-3.1	-3	-0.1	1
202	1937-01-03	VERNON	BC	1128582	-119.2	50.23	482	-6.9	-6.5	-0.4	1
203	1937-01-28	VERNON	BC	1128582	-119.2	50.23	482	-13.6	-13.4	-0.2	1

204	1938-12-25	VERNON	BC	1128582	-119.2	50.23	482	-5.4	-5	-0.4	1
205	1938-12-28	VERNON	BC	1128582	-119.2	50.23	482	-10.9	-10.6	-0.3	1
206	1939-01-05	VERNON	BC	1128582	-119.2	50.23	482	-2	-1.2	-0.8	1
207	1940-01-30	VERNON	BC	1128582	-119.2	50.23	482	-2.6	-2.4	-0.2	1
208	1940-11-08	VERNON	BC	1128582	-119.2	50.23	482	0.1	0.5	-0.4	1
209	1940-12-13	VERNON	BC	1128582	-119.2	50.23	482	-3.7	-3.5	-0.2	1
210	1941-12-11	VERNON	BC	1128582	-119.2	50.23	482	-0.5	-0.2	-0.3	1
211	1941-12-25	VERNON	BC	1128582	-119.2	50.23	482	-0.5	-0.3	-0.2	1
212	1941-12-26	VERNON	BC	1128582	-119.2	50.23	482	-2.6	-2.4	-0.2	1
213	1942-05-25	VERNON	BC	1128582	-119.2	50.23	482	13.6	14.1	-0.5	1
214	1943-01-15	VERNON	BC	1128582	-119.2	50.23	482	-2	-1.8	-0.2	1
215	1943-10-18	VERNON	BC	1128582	-119.2	50.23	482	9.3	9.4	-0.1	1
216	1944-05-23	VERNON	BC	1128582	-119.2	50.23	482	6.6	6.9	-0.3	1
217	1944-12-31	VERNON	BC	1128582	-119.2	50.23	482	-1	-0.7	-0.3	1
218	1946-06-06	VERNON	BC	1128582	-119.2	50.23	482	9.7	10.5	-0.8	1
219	1946-11-18	VERNON	BC	1128582	-119.2	50.23	482	-9.1	-8	-1.1	1
220	1947-02-11	VERNON	BC	1128582	-119.2	50.23	482	-3.7	-3	-0.7	1
221	1950-11-22	VERNON	BC	1128582	-119.2	50.23	482	-3.7	-3.5	-0.2	1
222	1951-01-03	VERNON	BC	1128582	-119.2	50.23	482	-4.2	-4	-0.2	1
223	1951-01-26	VERNON	BC	1128582	-119.2	50.23	482	-8.1	-7	-1.1	1
224	1951-12-30	VERNON	BC	1128582	-119.2	50.23	482	-15.4	-14.5	-0.9	1
225	1952-01-15	VERNON	BC	1128582	-119.2	50.23	482	-11.9	-11.7	-0.2	1
226	1952-01-21	VERNON	BC	1128582	-119.2	50.23	482	-5.9	-5	-0.9	1
227	1953-11-01	VERNON	BC	1128582	-119.2	50.23	482	6.6	6.9	-0.3	1
228	1954-01-15	VERNON	BC	1128582	-119.2	50.23	482	-16.5	-16.2	-0.3	1
229	1954-01-22	VERNON	BC	1128582	-119.2	50.23	482	-12.6	-12.3	-0.3	1
230	1954-05-11	VERNON	BC	1128582	-119.2	50.23	482	10.9	11.1	-0.2	1
231	1956-12-04	VERNON	BC	1128582	-119.2	50.23	482	-11.4	-11.2	-0.2	1
232	1957-01-08	VERNON	BC	1128582	-119.2	50.23	482	-8.6	-8	-0.6	1
233	1958-11-24	VERNON	BC	1128582	-119.2	50.23	482	-2	-1.8	-0.2	1
234	1958-12-06	VERNON	BC	1128582	-119.2	50.23	482	-8.1	-8	-0.1	1
235	1958-12-07	VERNON	BC	1128582	-119.2	50.23	482	-10.9	-10.7	-0.2	1
236	1959-04-23	VERNON	BC	1128582	-119.2	50.23	482	9.3	9.4	-0.1	1
237	1962-01-19	VERNON	BC	1128582	-119.2	50.23	482	-19.1	-17.8	-1.3	1

238	1962-01-20	VERNON	BC	1128582	-119.2	50.23	482	-16.5	-12.3	-4.2	1
239	1962-01-21	VERNON	BC	1128582	-119.2	50.23	482	-12.6	-11.2	-1.4	1
240	1962-01-22	VERNON	BC	1128582	-119.2	50.23	482	-8.6	-4.6	-4	1
241	1962-01-23	VERNON	BC	1128582	-119.2	50.23	482	-3.7	2.3	-6	1
242	1966-01-03	VERNON	BC	1128582	-119.2	50.23	482	-15.4	-15.1	-0.3	1
243	1972-05-06	VERNON	BC	1128582	-119.2	50.23	482	7.7	7.9	-0.2	1
244	1982-11-21	VERNON	BC	1128582	-119.2	50.23	482	-6.8	-6.7	-0.1	1
245	1984-12-16	VERNON	BC	1128582	-119.2	50.23	482	-9.8	-9	-0.8	1
246	1984-12-27	VERNON	BC	1128582	-119.2	50.23	482	-6.8	-6.7	-0.1	1
247	1985-01-11	VERNON	BC	1128582	-119.2	50.23	482	-3.3	-3.1	-0.2	1
248	1985-11-25	VERNON	BC	1128582	-119.2	50.23	482	-12.8	-12.4	-0.4	1
249	1985-11-26	VERNON	BC	1128582	-119.2	50.23	482	-19.8	-19.4	-0.4	1
250	1985-12-25	VERNON	BC	1128582	-119.2	50.23	482	-4.8	-4.5	-0.3	1
251	1987-12-30	VERNON	BC	1128582	-119.2	50.23	482	-3.3	-3.1	-0.2	1
252	1989-02-16	VERNON	BC	1128582	-119.2	50.23	482	-4.3	-4.1	-0.2	1
253	1989-12-20	VERNON	BC	1128582	-119.2	50.23	482	-1.4	-1	-0.4	1
254	1995-10-29	INUVIK	NWT	2202578	-133.48	68.3	103	-7.4	-6.9	-0.5	1
255	1888-12-23	MEDICINE HAT	ALTA	3034485	-110.72	50.02	715	-8.3	-8.2	-0.1	1
256	1995-11-16	MEDICINE HAT	ALTA	3034485	-110.72	50.02	715	-0.7	2.3	-3	1
257	2005-08-23	MEDICINE HAT	ALTA	3034485	-110.72	50.02	715	13.7	15	-1.3	1
258	1931-03-10	RANFURLY	ALTA	3015401	-111.73	53.42	687	-16.4	-15.6	-0.8	1
259	1933-02-10	RANFURLY	ALTA	3015401	-111.73	53.42	687	-29.7	-28.9	-0.8	1
260	1935-03-25	RANFURLY	ALTA	3015401	-111.73	53.42	687	-13.5	-13.3	-0.2	1
261	2008-12-01	RANFURLY	ALTA	3015401	-111.73	53.42	687	-5	-1.5	-3.5	1
262	2011-12-02	RANFURLY	ALTA	3015401	-111.73	53.42	687	-4	-1	-3	1
263	1896-02-13	NORTHBATTLEFORD	SASK	4045695	-108.25	52.77	548	-29.6	-28.9	-0.7	1
264	1906-04-24	NORTHBATTLEFORD	SASK	4045695	-108.25	52.77	548	7.3	7.8	-0.5	1
265	1906-12-04	NORTHBATTLEFORD	SASK	4045695	-108.25	52.77	548	-20.5	-19.4	-1.1	1
266	1907-02-01	NORTHBATTLEFORD	SASK	4045695	-108.25	52.77	548	-27.9	-27.8	-0.1	1
267	1910-12-27	NORTHBATTLEFORD	SASK	4045695	-108.25	52.77	548	-16.9	-16.7	-0.2	1
268	1911-01-09	NORTHBATTLEFORD	SASK	4045695	-108.25	52.77	548	-34	-33.9	-0.1	1
269	1911-07-01	NORTHBATTLEFORD	SASK	4045695	-108.25	52.77	548	11.6	12.2	-0.6	1
270	1911-09-16	NORTHBATTLEFORD	SASK	4045695	-108.25	52.77	548	8.6	8.9	-0.3	1
271	1912-07-13	NORTHBATTLEFORD	SASK	4045695	-108.25	52.77	548	12.2	13.3	-1.1	1

272	1913-10-27	NORTHBATTLEFORD	SASK	4045695	-108.25	52.77	548	-4.6	-3.9	-0.7	1
273	1920-01-14	NORTHBATTLEFORD	SASK	4045695	-108.25	52.77	548	-22.3	-22.2	-0.1	1
274	1923-01-01	NORTHBATTLEFORD	SASK	4045695	-108.25	52.77	548	-23.4	-23.3	-0.1	1
275	1926-12-02	NORTHBATTLEFORD	SASK	4045695	-108.25	52.77	548	-18.1	-17.8	-0.3	1
276	1927-02-01	NORTHBATTLEFORD	SASK	4045695	-108.25	52.77	548	-24.6	-24.4	-0.2	1
277	1930-01-04	NORTHBATTLEFORD	SASK	4045695	-108.25	52.77	548	-22.3	-21.7	-0.6	1
278	1933-12-31	NORTHBATTLEFORD	SASK	4045695	-108.25	52.77	548	-31.2	-31.1	-0.1	1
279	1929-04-28	NORTH BAY	ONT	6085701	-79.42	46.37	370	6.8	7.2	-0.4	1
280	1930-12-14	NORTH BAY	ONT	6085701	-79.42	46.37	370	-15.6	-13.9	-1.7	1
281	1931-01-13	NORTH BAY	ONT	6085701	-79.42	46.37	370	-16.7	-15	-1.7	1
282	1931-02-26	NORTH BAY	ONT	6085701	-79.42	46.37	370	-2.4	-2.2	-0.2	1
283	1932-04-11	NORTH BAY	ONT	6085701	-79.42	46.37	370	2.4	3.3	-0.9	1
284	1933-11-19	NORTH BAY	ONT	6085701	-79.42	46.37	370	-6.7	-6.1	-0.6	1
285	1934-01-11	NORTH BAY	ONT	6085701	-79.42	46.37	370	-1.2	-1.1	-0.1	1
286	1934-01-12	NORTH BAY	ONT	6085701	-79.42	46.37	370	-1.9	-1.7	-0.2	1
287	1934-01-13	NORTH BAY	ONT	6085701	-79.42	46.37	370	-2.4	-1.7	-0.7	1
288	1934-11-23	NORTH BAY	ONT	6085701	-79.42	46.37	370	-1.2	0	-1.2	1
289	1934-12-06	NORTH BAY	ONT	6085701	-79.42	46.37	370	-18	-16.7	-1.3	1
290	1934-12-16	NORTH BAY	ONT	6085701	-79.42	46.37	370	-3.5	-3.3	-0.2	1
291	1934-12-20	NORTH BAY	ONT	6085701	-79.42	46.37	370	-14.5	-13.3	-1.2	1
292	1934-12-23	NORTH BAY	ONT	6085701	-79.42	46.37	370	-13.3	-12.2	-1.1	1
293	1934-12-26	NORTH BAY	ONT	6085701	-79.42	46.37	370	-20.2	-20	-0.2	1
294	1934-12-29	NORTH BAY	ONT	6085701	-79.42	46.37	370	-18.5	-16.7	-1.8	1
295	1935-02-24	NORTH BAY	ONT	6085701	-79.42	46.37	370	-13.2	-8.3	-4.9	1
296	1935-02-25	NORTH BAY	ONT	6085701	-79.42	46.37	370	-14.5	-14.4	-0.1	1
297	1876-12-31	QUEBEC	QUE	701S001	-71.38	46.8	60	-12.8	-12.3	-0.5	1
298	1883-10-12	QUEBEC	QUE	701S001	-71.38	46.8	60	8.9	9	-0.1	1
299	1889-04-27	QUEBEC	QUE	701S001	-71.38	46.8	60	4.4	4.5	-0.1	1
300	1898-05-11	QUEBEC	QUE	701S001	-71.38	46.8	60	6.7	7.1	-0.4	1
301	1898-11-19	QUEBEC	QUE	701S001	-71.38	46.8	60	2.8	2.9	-0.1	1
302	1899-09-20	QUEBEC	QUE	701S001	-71.38	46.8	60	10.6	10.9	-0.3	1
303	1904-02-07	QUEBEC	QUE	701S001	-71.38	46.8	60	-13.3	-12.9	-0.4	1
304	1904-05-16	QUEBEC	QUE	701S001	-71.38	46.8	60	9.4	9.7	-0.3	1
305	1905-11-08	QUEBEC	QUE	701S001	-71.38	46.8	60	1.1	1.4	-0.3	1

306	1908-11-11	QUEBEC	QUE	701S001	-71.38	46.8	60	2.8	2.9	-0.1	1
307	1910-06-06	QUEBEC	QUE	701S001	-71.38	46.8	60	8.3	8.4	-0.1	1
308	1915-10-30	QUEBEC	QUE	701S001	-71.38	46.8	60	8.3	8.4	-0.1	1
309	1918-01-10	QUEBEC	QUE	701S001	-71.38	46.8	60	-11.7	-11.5	-0.2	1
310	1918-09-06	QUEBEC	QUE	701S001	-71.38	46.8	60	12.2	12.3	-0.1	1
311	1918-09-12	QUEBEC	QUE	701S001	-71.38	46.8	60	9.4	9.7	-0.3	1
312	1919-09-12	QUEBEC	QUE	701S001	-71.38	46.8	60	12.8	13.1	-0.3	1
313	1943-01-29	QUEBEC	QUE	701S001	-71.38	46.8	60	-10.6	-10.1	-0.5	1
314	1943-06-03	QUEBEC	QUE	701S001	-71.38	46.8	60	10.6	10.9	-0.3	1
315	1944-12-24	QUEBEC	QUE	701S001	-71.38	46.8	60	-9.4	-9	-0.4	1
316	1953-01-16	QUEBEC	QUE	701S001	-71.38	46.8	60	-13.3	-13	-0.3	1
317	2011-11-04	FORT NELSON	BC	1192946	-122.6	58.83	382	-18.2	-9.9	-8.3	1
318	1914-12-03	MORRISBURG	ONT	6105460	-75.18	44.92	82	4.4	4.6	-0.2	1
319	1916-11-21	MORRISBURG	ONT	6105460	-75.18	44.92	82	-1	-0.9	-0.1	1
320	1919-11-08	MORRISBURG	ONT	6105460	-75.18	44.92	82	2	2.3	-0.3	1
321	1919-11-24	MORRISBURG	ONT	6105460	-75.18	44.92	82	-3.6	-3.2	-0.4	1
322	1928-12-04	MORRISBURG	ONT	6105460	-75.18	44.92	82	2.6	3	-0.4	1
323	1930-11-25	MORRISBURG	ONT	6105460	-75.18	44.92	82	2.6	3.5	-0.9	1
324	1935-09-27	MORRISBURG	ONT	6105460	-75.18	44.92	82	8.9	9.4	-0.5	1
325	1935-12-15	MORRISBURG	ONT	6105460	-75.18	44.92	82	-1.1	-0.8	-0.3	1
326	1944-03-16	MORRISBURG	ONT	6105460	-75.18	44.92	82	-2.3	-1.8	-0.5	1
327	1946-11-03	MORRISBURG	ONT	6105460	-75.18	44.92	82	6.1	6.2	-0.1	1
328	1950-01-23	MORRISBURG	ONT	6105460	-75.18	44.92	82	-5.3	-3.9	-1.4	1
329	1952-12-05	MORRISBURG	ONT	6105460	-75.18	44.92	82	3.1	3.5	-0.4	1
330	1952-12-25	MORRISBURG	ONT	6105460	-75.18	44.92	82	1.6	1.7	-0.1	1
331	1955-12-16	MORRISBURG	ONT	6105460	-75.18	44.92	82	-3.5	-3.3	-0.2	1
332	1956-12-20	MORRISBURG	ONT	6105460	-75.18	44.92	82	0.1	0.5	-0.4	1
333	1957-11-04	MORRISBURG	ONT	6105460	-75.18	44.92	82	4.9	5.2	-0.3	1
334	1962-03-13	MORRISBURG	ONT	6105460	-75.18	44.92	82	0	0.1	-0.1	1
335	1963-11-16	MORRISBURG	ONT	6105460	-75.18	44.92	82	5	5.2	-0.2	1
336	1964-12-25	MORRISBURG	ONT	6105460	-75.18	44.92	82	8.9	9.1	-0.2	1
337	1967-01-28	MORRISBURG	ONT	6105460	-75.18	44.92	82	-5.6	-5.4	-0.2	1
338	1967-05-15	MORRISBURG	ONT	6105460	-75.18	44.92	82	8.9	9.1	-0.2	1
339	1967-12-26	MORRISBURG	ONT	6105460	-75.18	44.92	82	-15	-14.8	-0.2	1

340	1968-11-29	MORRISBURG	ONT	6105460	-75.18	44.92	82	-0.6	-0.4	-0.2	1
341	1969-09-17	MORRISBURG	ONT	6105460	-75.18	44.92	82	11.7	11.9	-0.2	1
342	1970-08-23	MORRISBURG	ONT	6105460	-75.18	44.92	82	13.9	14	-0.1	1
343	1970-11-13	MORRISBURG	ONT	6105460	-75.18	44.92	82	8.3	9.5	-1.2	1
344	1970-11-14	MORRISBURG	ONT	6105460	-75.18	44.92	82	2.2	2.5	-0.3	1
345	1970-11-15	MORRISBURG	ONT	6105460	-75.18	44.92	82	1.1	1.4	-0.3	1
346	1970-11-28	MORRISBURG	ONT	6105460	-75.18	44.92	82	1.1	2	-0.9	1
347	1970-11-30	MORRISBURG	ONT	6105460	-75.18	44.92	82	1.1	2	-0.9	1
348	1971-01-27	MORRISBURG	ONT	6105460	-75.18	44.92	82	-20	-19.3	-0.7	1
349	1971-03-04	MORRISBURG	ONT	6105460	-75.18	44.92	82	-4.4	-4.2	-0.2	1
350	1971-11-11	MORRISBURG	ONT	6105460	-75.18	44.92	82	-0.6	-0.4	-0.2	1
351	1972-11-04	MORRISBURG	ONT	6105460	-75.18	44.92	82	0	0.2	-0.2	1
352	1973-03-09	MORRISBURG	ONT	6105460	-75.18	44.92	82	-0.6	-0.4	-0.2	1
353	1973-10-16	MORRISBURG	ONT	6105460	-75.18	44.92	82	4.4	4.6	-0.2	1
354	1974-02-20	MORRISBURG	ONT	6105460	-75.18	44.92	82	0	0.2	-0.2	1
355	1974-03-01	MORRISBURG	ONT	6105460	-75.18	44.92	82	2.8	3	-0.2	1
356	1974-03-17	MORRISBURG	ONT	6105460	-75.18	44.92	82	-2.8	-1.5	-1.3	1
357	1975-03-20	MORRISBURG	ONT	6105460	-75.18	44.92	82	1.7	2	-0.3	1
358	1975-11-13	MORRISBURG	ONT	6105460	-75.18	44.92	82	7.2	7.6	-0.4	1
359	1975-11-14	MORRISBURG	ONT	6105460	-75.18	44.92	82	-1.7	-0.9	-0.8	1
360	1976-10-07	MORRISBURG	ONT	6105460	-75.18	44.92	82	10	10.1	-0.1	1
361	1976-10-08	MORRISBURG	ONT	6105460	-75.18	44.92	82	6.7	7.1	-0.4	1
362	1977-02-12	MORRISBURG	ONT	6105460	-75.18	44.92	82	2.2	2.5	-0.3	1
363	1977-11-17	MORRISBURG	ONT	6105460	-75.18	44.92	82	8.9	9.1	-0.2	1
364	1979-01-29	MORRISBURG	ONT	6105460	-75.18	44.92	82	-5	-4.6	-0.4	1
365	1979-12-26	MORRISBURG	ONT	6105460	-75.18	44.92	82	-0.5	-0.3	-0.2	1
366	1980-03-11	MORRISBURG	ONT	6105460	-75.18	44.92	82	-5	-4.6	-0.4	1
367	1980-03-18	MORRISBURG	ONT	6105460	-75.18	44.92	82	1	1.4	-0.4	1
368	1982-09-27	MORRISBURG	ONT	6105460	-75.18	44.92	82	14	14.1	-0.1	1
369	1982-11-04	MORRISBURG	ONT	6105460	-75.18	44.92	82	10.5	10.8	-0.3	1
370	1983-11-05	MORRISBURG	ONT	6105460	-75.18	44.92	82	1.5	2.4	-0.9	1
371	1983-11-16	MORRISBURG	ONT	6105460	-75.18	44.92	82	1	1.9	-0.9	1
372	1983-11-17	MORRISBURG	ONT	6105460	-75.18	44.92	82	-1	-0.8	-0.2	1
373	1983-12-13	MORRISBURG	ONT	6105460	-75.18	44.92	82	1	1.4	-0.4	1

374	1984-04-24	MORRISBURG	ONT	6105460	-75.18	44.92	82	8	8.8	-0.8	1
375	1984-05-08	MORRISBURG	ONT	6105460	-75.18	44.92	82	12	13.3	-1.3	1
376	1984-11-11	MORRISBURG	ONT	6105460	-75.18	44.92	82	10.5	10.8	-0.3	1
377	1984-11-16	MORRISBURG	ONT	6105460	-75.18	44.92	82	4.5	5.4	-0.9	1
378	1985-02-23	MORRISBURG	ONT	6105460	-75.18	44.92	82	3	3.3	-0.3	1
379	1985-05-05	MORRISBURG	ONT	6105460	-75.18	44.92	82	6	7.5	-1.5	1
380	1985-11-10	MORRISBURG	ONT	6105460	-75.18	44.92	82	0.5	1.4	-0.9	1
381	1985-11-28	MORRISBURG	ONT	6105460	-75.18	44.92	82	-5	-4.6	-0.4	1
382	1985-12-08	MORRISBURG	ONT	6105460	-75.18	44.92	82	0	0.8	-0.8	1
383	1986-01-21	MORRISBURG	ONT	6105460	-75.18	44.92	82	-2	-1.7	-0.3	1
384	1987-01-10	MORRISBURG	ONT	6105460	-75.18	44.92	82	-3	-1.7	-1.3	1
385	1988-10-22	MORRISBURG	ONT	6105460	-75.18	44.92	82	-0.5	0.3	-0.8	1
386	1990-02-25	MORRISBURG	ONT	6105460	-75.18	44.92	82	-17	-16.9	-0.1	1
387	1979-10-29	RED LAKE	ONT	6016970	-93.8	51.07	386	1.8	2	-0.2	1
388	1983-11-19	RED LAKE	ONT	6016970	-93.8	51.07	386	1.7	1.9	-0.2	1
389	2015-01-23	RED LAKE	ONT	6016970	-93.8	51.07	386	-14	-4.8	-9.2	1
390	2015-01-28	RED LAKE	ONT	6016970	-93.8	51.07	386	-15.7	-5.4	-10.3	1
391	1910-01-05	MONT JOLI	QUE	7055121	-68.2	48.6	52	-15.6	-15.3	-0.3	1
392	2004-05-09	MONT JOLI	QUE	7055121	-68.2	48.6	52	2	2.7	-0.7	1
393	1977-02-18	SUSSEX	NB	8105200	-65.53	45.72	21	-2.2	-1.9	-0.3	1
394	2007-03-06	SUSSEX	NB	8105200	-65.53	45.72	21	-17.5	-13.5	-4	1
395	1890-09-12	LONDON	ONT	6144478	-81.15	43.03	278	17.8	18	-0.2	1
396	1897-02-09	LONDON	ONT	6144478	-81.15	43.03	278	-1.9	-1.7	-0.2	1
397	1911-12-18	LONDON	ONT	6144478	-81.15	43.03	278	-0.7	-0.6	-0.1	1
398	1933-10-22	LONDON	ONT	6144478	-81.15	43.03	278	4.7	5.2	-0.5	1
399	1935-12-11	LONDON	ONT	6144478	-81.15	43.03	278	-0.6	-0.4	-0.2	1
400	1938-04-08	LONDON	ONT	6144478	-81.15	43.03	278	0	0.6	-0.6	1
401	1942-11-29	LONDON	ONT	6144478	-81.15	43.03	278	-2.1	-1.7	-0.4	1
402	2016-01-26	LONDON	ONT	6144478	-81.15	43.03	278	-0.6	0	-0.6	1
403	2015-10-30	BLUE RIVER	BC	1160899	-119.28	52.13	690	3.5	3.8	-0.3	1
404	1941-04-14	WILLIAMS LAKE	BC	1098941	-122.05	52.18	940	5.2	5.6	-0.4	1
405	1941-06-24	WILLIAMS LAKE	BC	1098941	-122.05	52.18	940	10	10.4	-0.4	1
406	1941-08-23	WILLIAMS LAKE	BC	1098941	-122.05	52.18	940	11.6	12	-0.4	1
407	1945-09-20	WILLIAMS LAKE	BC	1098941	-122.05	52.18	940	5.2	6.7	-1.5	1

408	1948-01-22	WILLIAMS LAKE	BC	1098941	-122.05	52.18	940	-0.8	-0.7	-0.1	1
409	1948-10-10	WILLIAMS LAKE	BC	1098941	-122.05	52.18	940	11.2	12.8	-1.6	1
410	1949-11-26	WILLIAMS LAKE	BC	1098941	-122.05	52.18	940	3.7	5.1	-1.4	1
411	1950-03-16	WILLIAMS LAKE	BC	1098941	-122.05	52.18	940	2.3	2.7	-0.4	1
412	1950-04-06	WILLIAMS LAKE	BC	1098941	-122.05	52.18	940	-3.6	-3.5	-0.1	1
413	1951-03-29	WILLIAMS LAKE	BC	1098941	-122.05	52.18	940	5.1	6.2	-1.1	1
414	1952-12-15	WILLIAMS LAKE	BC	1098941	-122.05	52.18	940	-2.3	-2	-0.3	1
415	1955-02-16	WILLIAMS LAKE	BC	1098941	-122.05	52.18	940	-1.9	-1.5	-0.4	1
416	1956-06-04	WILLIAMS LAKE	BC	1098941	-122.05	52.18	940	9.2	9.5	-0.3	1
417	1957-06-08	WILLIAMS LAKE	BC	1098941	-122.05	52.18	940	11.2	12.2	-1	1
418	1957-12-17	WILLIAMS LAKE	BC	1098941	-122.05	52.18	940	3.2	3.3	-0.1	1
419	1958-10-31	WILLIAMS LAKE	BC	1098941	-122.05	52.18	940	12.2	12.8	-0.6	1
420	1959-09-15	WILLIAMS LAKE	BC	1098941	-122.05	52.18	940	8.2	8.7	-0.5	1
421	1890-02-13	INDIAN HEAD	SASK	4013480	-103.65	50.55	579	-26.1	-24.2	-1.9	1
422	1924-04-09	INDIAN HEAD	SASK	4013480	-103.65	50.55	579	-2.6	-1.9	-0.7	1
423	1937-12-21	INDIAN HEAD	SASK	4013480	-103.65	50.55	579	-1.5	-1.3	-0.2	1
424	1939-10-15	INDIAN HEAD	SASK	4013480	-103.65	50.55	579	-0.9	-0.7	-0.2	1
425	1941-11-27	INDIAN HEAD	SASK	4013480	-103.65	50.55	579	-3.8	-3.5	-0.3	1
426	1942-11-04	INDIAN HEAD	SASK	4013480	-103.65	50.55	579	-4.9	-4.8	-0.1	1
427	1967-10-06	INDIAN HEAD	SASK	4013480	-103.65	50.55	579	-0.4	-0.2	-0.2	1
428	1970-11-03	INDIAN HEAD	SASK	4013480	-103.65	50.55	579	-2.1	-1.9	-0.2	1
429	1972-03-25	INDIAN HEAD	SASK	4013480	-103.65	50.55	579	-2.1	-1.8	-0.3	1
430	1978-04-06	INDIAN HEAD	SASK	4013480	-103.65	50.55	579	-1.5	-0.8	-0.7	1
431	1982-10-18	INDIAN HEAD	SASK	4013480	-103.65	50.55	579	-1.5	-1.2	-0.3	1
432	1983-03-05	INDIAN HEAD	SASK	4013480	-103.65	50.55	579	-4.6	-4.4	-0.2	1
433	1983-05-14	INDIAN HEAD	SASK	4013480	-103.65	50.55	579	-2	-1.2	-0.8	1
434	1984-10-16	INDIAN HEAD	SASK	4013480	-103.65	50.55	579	-3	-2.3	-0.7	1
435	1987-03-07	INDIAN HEAD	SASK	4013480	-103.65	50.55	579	-2	-1.7	-0.3	1
436	1988-02-19	INDIAN HEAD	SASK	4013480	-103.65	50.55	579	-4.1	-3.8	-0.3	1
437	1988-12-06	INDIAN HEAD	SASK	4013480	-103.65	50.55	579	-4.6	-4.5	-0.1	1
438	1989-11-21	INDIAN HEAD	SASK	4013480	-103.65	50.55	579	-4.6	-4.5	-0.1	1
439	1989-12-05	INDIAN HEAD	SASK	4013480	-103.65	50.55	579	-3.6	-3	-0.6	1
440	1991-12-22	INDIAN HEAD	SASK	4013480	-103.65	50.55	579	-3.6	-3	-0.6	1
441	1995-12-01	INDIAN HEAD	SASK	4013480	-103.65	50.55	579	-11.9	0	-11.9	1

442	1995-12-06	INDIAN HEAD	SASK	4013480	-103.65	50.55	579	-16.2	0	-16.2	1
443	1995-12-07	INDIAN HEAD	SASK	4013480	-103.65	50.55	579	-19.6	0	-19.6	1
444	1995-12-08	INDIAN HEAD	SASK	4013480	-103.65	50.55	579	-25.6	0	-25.6	1
445	1995-12-09	INDIAN HEAD	SASK	4013480	-103.65	50.55	579	-21.9	0	-21.9	1
446	1995-12-15	INDIAN HEAD	SASK	4013480	-103.65	50.55	579	-16.3	0	-16.3	1
447	1913-10-02	LA POCATIERE	QUE	7054096	-70.03	47.35	31	7.4	8.4	-1	1
448	1913-10-15	LA POCATIERE	QUE	7054096	-70.03	47.35	31	5.4	8.5	-3.1	1
449	1913-10-16	LA POCATIERE	QUE	7054096	-70.03	47.35	31	7.4	9.3	-1.9	1
450	1913-10-17	LA POCATIERE	QUE	7054096	-70.03	47.35	31	6.2	8.5	-2.3	1
451	1913-10-24	LA POCATIERE	QUE	7054096	-70.03	47.35	31	8.7	11	-2.3	1
452	1913-10-27	LA POCATIERE	QUE	7054096	-70.03	47.35	31	7.4	7.7	-0.3	1
453	1913-11-01	LA POCATIERE	QUE	7054096	-70.03	47.35	31	-4.7	-4.2	-0.5	1
454	1913-11-13	LA POCATIERE	QUE	7054096	-70.03	47.35	31	2	2.1	-0.1	1
455	1913-11-29	LA POCATIERE	QUE	7054096	-70.03	47.35	31	-0.6	0.1	-0.7	1
456	1913-12-27	LA POCATIERE	QUE	7054096	-70.03	47.35	31	-17.6	-16.9	-0.7	1
457	1914-01-06	LA POCATIERE	QUE	7054096	-70.03	47.35	31	-9.6	-8.9	-0.7	1
458	1914-01-14	LA POCATIERE	QUE	7054096	-70.03	47.35	31	-32.6	-28.2	-4.4	1
459	1914-01-15	LA POCATIERE	QUE	7054096	-70.03	47.35	31	-21.5	-20.9	-0.6	1
460	1914-01-20	LA POCATIERE	QUE	7054096	-70.03	47.35	31	-26.5	-22.7	-3.8	1
461	1914-02-07	LA POCATIERE	QUE	7054096	-70.03	47.35	31	-15.4	-14.5	-0.9	1
462	1914-02-12	LA POCATIERE	QUE	7054096	-70.03	47.35	31	-32.1	-31.6	-0.5	1
463	1914-11-14	LA POCATIERE	QUE	7054096	-70.03	47.35	31	-3	-2.1	-0.9	1
464	1914-11-18	LA POCATIERE	QUE	7054096	-70.03	47.35	31	-16.5	-14	-2.5	1
465	1914-12-04	LA POCATIERE	QUE	7054096	-70.03	47.35	31	-6.5	-6.1	-0.4	1
466	1914-12-16	LA POCATIERE	QUE	7054096	-70.03	47.35	31	-17.6	-16.2	-1.4	1
467	1914-12-17	LA POCATIERE	QUE	7054096	-70.03	47.35	31	-15.4	-14.5	-0.9	1
468	1915-01-22	LA POCATIERE	QUE	7054096	-70.03	47.35	31	-13.2	-13.1	-0.1	1
469	1915-01-23	LA POCATIERE	QUE	7054096	-70.03	47.35	31	-16	-14.5	-1.5	1
470	1915-01-29	LA POCATIERE	QUE	7054096	-70.03	47.35	31	-10.2	-8.9	-1.3	1
471	1915-02-26	LA POCATIERE	QUE	7054096	-70.03	47.35	31	-4.8	-4.6	-0.2	1
472	1915-02-27	LA POCATIERE	QUE	7054096	-70.03	47.35	31	-4.7	-4.6	-0.1	1
473	1915-02-28	LA POCATIERE	QUE	7054096	-70.03	47.35	31	-6.4	-6.2	-0.2	1
474	1915-04-01	LA POCATIERE	QUE	7054096	-70.03	47.35	31	2	2.9	-0.9	1
475	1915-04-08	LA POCATIERE	QUE	7054096	-70.03	47.35	31	4	6.1	-2.1	1

476	1915-04-10	LA POCATIERE	QUE	7054096	-70.03	47.35	31	0.2	1	-0.8	1
477	1915-04-29	LA POCATIERE	QUE	7054096	-70.03	47.35	31	7.4	11.8	-4.4	1
478	1915-04-30	LA POCATIERE	QUE	7054096	-70.03	47.35	31	4.8	5.3	-0.5	1
479	1915-05-01	LA POCATIERE	QUE	7054096	-70.03	47.35	31	1.6	3	-1.4	1
480	1915-05-02	LA POCATIERE	QUE	7054096	-70.03	47.35	31	1.6	1.8	-0.2	1
481	1915-05-18	LA POCATIERE	QUE	7054096	-70.03	47.35	31	10	10.4	-0.4	1
482	1915-05-28	LA POCATIERE	QUE	7054096	-70.03	47.35	31	9.6	10	-0.4	1
483	1915-06-23	LA POCATIERE	QUE	7054096	-70.03	47.35	31	7.4	11	-3.6	1
484	1915-08-09	LA POCATIERE	QUE	7054096	-70.03	47.35	31	13	13.3	-0.3	1
485	1915-09-22	LA POCATIERE	QUE	7054096	-70.03	47.35	31	8.8	9.2	-0.4	1
486	1915-09-26	LA POCATIERE	QUE	7054096	-70.03	47.35	31	4	4.7	-0.7	1
487	1915-09-29	LA POCATIERE	QUE	7054096	-70.03	47.35	31	9.7	10.5	-0.8	1
488	1915-10-30	LA POCATIERE	QUE	7054096	-70.03	47.35	31	6.7	7.8	-1.1	1
489	1915-10-31	LA POCATIERE	QUE	7054096	-70.03	47.35	31	9.2	10.5	-1.3	1
490	1915-11-04	LA POCATIERE	QUE	7054096	-70.03	47.35	31	2.6	4	-1.4	1
491	1915-11-06	LA POCATIERE	QUE	7054096	-70.03	47.35	31	-1.2	-0.6	-0.6	1
492	1915-11-13	LA POCATIERE	QUE	7054096	-70.03	47.35	31	4	4.7	-0.7	1
493	1915-11-22	LA POCATIERE	QUE	7054096	-70.03	47.35	31	1.5	4.7	-3.2	1
494	1915-11-30	LA POCATIERE	QUE	7054096	-70.03	47.35	31	1.5	4.1	-2.6	1
495	1915-12-05	LA POCATIERE	QUE	7054096	-70.03	47.35	31	-0.2	1	-1.2	1
496	1915-12-08	LA POCATIERE	QUE	7054096	-70.03	47.35	31	-6.3	-4.1	-2.2	1
497	1915-12-09	LA POCATIERE	QUE	7054096	-70.03	47.35	31	-4.8	-4.6	-0.2	1
498	1915-12-20	LA POCATIERE	QUE	7054096	-70.03	47.35	31	-6.5	-4.6	-1.9	1
499	1916-01-02	LA POCATIERE	QUE	7054096	-70.03	47.35	31	-16.5	-13.1	-3.4	1
500	1916-01-03	LA POCATIERE	QUE	7054096	-70.03	47.35	31	-12.6	-12.2	-0.4	1
501	1916-01-04	LA POCATIERE	QUE	7054096	-70.03	47.35	31	-12	-11.1	-0.9	1
502	1916-01-07	LA POCATIERE	QUE	7054096	-70.03	47.35	31	-15.4	-13.1	-2.3	1
503	1916-01-08	LA POCATIERE	QUE	7054096	-70.03	47.35	31	-16	-15.1	-0.9	1
504	1916-01-09	LA POCATIERE	QUE	7054096	-70.03	47.35	31	-14.3	-12.1	-2.2	1
505	1916-01-17	LA POCATIERE	QUE	7054096	-70.03	47.35	31	-10.2	-10	-0.2	1
506	1916-01-19	LA POCATIERE	QUE	7054096	-70.03	47.35	31	-14.9	-10.5	-4.4	1
507	1916-01-23	LA POCATIERE	QUE	7054096	-70.03	47.35	31	-6.4	-5.1	-1.3	1
508	1916-01-27	LA POCATIERE	QUE	7054096	-70.03	47.35	31	-14.3	-14	-0.3	1
509	1916-01-28	LA POCATIERE	QUE	7054096	-70.03	47.35	31	-12	-10.5	-1.5	1

510	1916-01-29	LA POCATIERE	QUE	7054096	-70.03	47.35	31	-15.4	-12.1	-3.3	1
511	1916-03-08	LA POCATIERE	QUE	7054096	-70.03	47.35	31	-10.8	-10.5	-0.3	1
512	1916-03-09	LA POCATIERE	QUE	7054096	-70.03	47.35	31	-10.8	-8.3	-2.5	1
513	1916-03-16	LA POCATIERE	QUE	7054096	-70.03	47.35	31	-14.9	-14.5	-0.4	1
514	1916-03-20	LA POCATIERE	QUE	7054096	-70.03	47.35	31	-13.8	-13.6	-0.2	1
515	1916-04-18	LA POCATIERE	QUE	7054096	-70.03	47.35	31	3.2	3.4	-0.2	1
516	1916-07-04	LA POCATIERE	QUE	7054096	-70.03	47.35	31	11.9	14.4	-2.5	1
517	1916-07-27	LA POCATIERE	QUE	7054096	-70.03	47.35	31	22.5	23	-0.5	1
518	1916-09-06	LA POCATIERE	QUE	7054096	-70.03	47.35	31	15.5	15.8	-0.3	1
519	1916-09-24	LA POCATIERE	QUE	7054096	-70.03	47.35	31	13.6	13.8	-0.2	1
520	1916-09-25	LA POCATIERE	QUE	7054096	-70.03	47.35	31	13.6	14.3	-0.7	1
521	1916-09-26	LA POCATIERE	QUE	7054096	-70.03	47.35	31	14.3	14.4	-0.1	1
522	1916-10-08	LA POCATIERE	QUE	7054096	-70.03	47.35	31	10.9	12.1	-1.2	1
523	1916-10-19	LA POCATIERE	QUE	7054096	-70.03	47.35	31	0.7	1.1	-0.4	1
524	1917-01-22	LA POCATIERE	QUE	7054096	-70.03	47.35	31	-19.3	-17	-2.3	1
525	1917-01-26	LA POCATIERE	QUE	7054096	-70.03	47.35	31	-21	-19.7	-1.3	1
526	1917-01-27	LA POCATIERE	QUE	7054096	-70.03	47.35	31	-21	-17	-4	1
527	1917-01-30	LA POCATIERE	QUE	7054096	-70.03	47.35	31	-3.2	-3.1	-0.1	1
528	1917-02-09	LA POCATIERE	QUE	7054096	-70.03	47.35	31	-14.3	-11.1	-3.2	1
529	1917-03-04	LA POCATIERE	QUE	7054096	-70.03	47.35	31	-12	-9.4	-2.6	1
530	1917-03-05	LA POCATIERE	QUE	7054096	-70.03	47.35	31	-14.9	-12.6	-2.3	1
531	1917-03-18	LA POCATIERE	QUE	7054096	-70.03	47.35	31	-0.7	0.8	-1.5	1
532	1917-03-19	LA POCATIERE	QUE	7054096	-70.03	47.35	31	-10.2	-8.9	-1.3	1
533	1917-03-25	LA POCATIERE	QUE	7054096	-70.03	47.35	31	2	3.4	-1.4	1
534	1917-03-27	LA POCATIERE	QUE	7054096	-70.03	47.35	31	1.6	2.2	-0.6	1
535	1917-04-10	LA POCATIERE	QUE	7054096	-70.03	47.35	31	-8.8	-5.6	-3.2	1
536	1917-04-17	LA POCATIERE	QUE	7054096	-70.03	47.35	31	3.2	3.3	-0.1	1
537	1917-04-29	LA POCATIERE	QUE	7054096	-70.03	47.35	31	3.2	5.4	-2.2	1
538	1917-04-30	LA POCATIERE	QUE	7054096	-70.03	47.35	31	1.6	3.2	-1.6	1
539	1917-05-15	LA POCATIERE	QUE	7054096	-70.03	47.35	31	7.3	7.6	-0.3	1
540	1917-05-23	LA POCATIERE	QUE	7054096	-70.03	47.35	31	5.4	6.9	-1.5	1
541	1917-10-11	LA POCATIERE	QUE	7054096	-70.03	47.35	31	3.3	6	-2.7	1
542	1917-11-03	LA POCATIERE	QUE	7054096	-70.03	47.35	31	2.6	2.9	-0.3	1
543	1917-11-11	LA POCATIERE	QUE	7054096	-70.03	47.35	31	0.6	0.9	-0.3	1

544	1917-11-22	LA POCATIERE	QUE	7054096	-70.03	47.35	31	-6.5	-4.2	-2.3	1
545	1917-12-14	LA POCATIERE	QUE	7054096	-70.03	47.35	31	-14.3	-13.6	-0.7	1
546	1917-12-15	LA POCATIERE	QUE	7054096	-70.03	47.35	31	-17.1	-17	-0.1	1
547	1917-12-17	LA POCATIERE	QUE	7054096	-70.03	47.35	31	-17.6	-14	-3.6	1
548	1917-12-18	LA POCATIERE	QUE	7054096	-70.03	47.35	31	-13.8	-12.6	-1.2	1
549	1917-12-19	LA POCATIERE	QUE	7054096	-70.03	47.35	31	-17.6	-17	-0.6	1
550	1917-12-28	LA POCATIERE	QUE	7054096	-70.03	47.35	31	-31	-29.9	-1.1	1
551	1918-01-09	LA POCATIERE	QUE	7054096	-70.03	47.35	31	-14.9	-13.1	-1.8	1
552	1918-01-15	LA POCATIERE	QUE	7054096	-70.03	47.35	31	-14.3	-13.1	-1.2	1
553	1918-01-30	LA POCATIERE	QUE	7054096	-70.03	47.35	31	-14.9	-12.6	-2.3	1
554	1918-02-11	LA POCATIERE	QUE	7054096	-70.03	47.35	31	-13.2	-13.1	-0.1	1
555	1918-02-21	LA POCATIERE	QUE	7054096	-70.03	47.35	31	-14.3	-12.1	-2.2	1
556	1918-02-27	LA POCATIERE	QUE	7054096	-70.03	47.35	31	-11.4	-10	-1.4	1
557	1918-03-07	LA POCATIERE	QUE	7054096	-70.03	47.35	31	-16	-13.9	-2.1	1
558	1918-04-04	LA POCATIERE	QUE	7054096	-70.03	47.35	31	-1.8	-0.6	-1.2	1
559	1918-04-10	LA POCATIERE	QUE	7054096	-70.03	47.35	31	-1.2	-0.6	-0.6	1
560	1918-04-18	LA POCATIERE	QUE	7054096	-70.03	47.35	31	-1.8	-1.7	-0.1	1
561	1918-05-16	LA POCATIERE	QUE	7054096	-70.03	47.35	31	10.1	11.3	-1.2	1
562	1918-10-05	LA POCATIERE	QUE	7054096	-70.03	47.35	31	-0.2	2.1	-2.3	1
563	1918-10-06	LA POCATIERE	QUE	7054096	-70.03	47.35	31	0.7	3	-2.3	1
564	1918-11-19	LA POCATIERE	QUE	7054096	-70.03	47.35	31	-0.2	0	-0.2	1
565	1918-12-02	LA POCATIERE	QUE	7054096	-70.03	47.35	31	-12	-10	-2	1
566	1919-01-05	LA POCATIERE	QUE	7054096	-70.03	47.35	31	-16	-14.5	-1.5	1
567	1919-01-06	LA POCATIERE	QUE	7054096	-70.03	47.35	31	-17.1	-13.9	-3.2	1
568	1919-01-25	LA POCATIERE	QUE	7054096	-70.03	47.35	31	-9.5	-5.1	-4.4	1
569	1919-01-28	LA POCATIERE	QUE	7054096	-70.03	47.35	31	-10.2	-9.4	-0.8	1
570	1919-01-31	LA POCATIERE	QUE	7054096	-70.03	47.35	31	-12	-10.5	-1.5	1
571	1919-02-18	LA POCATIERE	QUE	7054096	-70.03	47.35	31	-9.6	-7.7	-1.9	1
572	1919-03-10	LA POCATIERE	QUE	7054096	-70.03	47.35	31	-8.8	-6.6	-2.2	1
573	1919-03-31	LA POCATIERE	QUE	7054096	-70.03	47.35	31	-4.7	-3.6	-1.1	1
574	1919-04-13	LA POCATIERE	QUE	7054096	-70.03	47.35	31	2	2.9	-0.9	1
575	1919-04-14	LA POCATIERE	QUE	7054096	-70.03	47.35	31	0.6	4.8	-4.2	1
576	1919-04-15	LA POCATIERE	QUE	7054096	-70.03	47.35	31	1	3	-2	1
577	1919-04-16	LA POCATIERE	QUE	7054096	-70.03	47.35	31	2	4.8	-2.8	1

578	1919-04-17	LA POCATIERE	QUE	7054096	-70.03	47.35	31	1	4	-3	1
579	1919-04-24	LA POCATIERE	QUE	7054096	-70.03	47.35	31	-2.4	-1.1	-1.3	1
580	1919-04-25	LA POCATIERE	QUE	7054096	-70.03	47.35	31	-1.2	0.3	-1.5	1
581	1919-04-26	LA POCATIERE	QUE	7054096	-70.03	47.35	31	0.2	1.1	-0.9	1
582	1919-05-02	LA POCATIERE	QUE	7054096	-70.03	47.35	31	4	4.7	-0.7	1
583	1919-06-06	LA POCATIERE	QUE	7054096	-70.03	47.35	31	14.8	15.8	-1	1
584	1919-11-26	LA POCATIERE	QUE	7054096	-70.03	47.35	31	-6.4	-4.1	-2.3	1
585	1919-11-28	LA POCATIERE	QUE	7054096	-70.03	47.35	31	-0.1	0.1	-0.2	1
586	1919-11-29	LA POCATIERE	QUE	7054096	-70.03	47.35	31	0.3	1.9	-1.6	1
587	1920-03-07	LA POCATIERE	QUE	7054096	-70.03	47.35	31	-16	-15	-1	1
588	1920-04-24	LA POCATIERE	QUE	7054096	-70.03	47.35	31	2	3.4	-1.4	1
589	1920-06-02	LA POCATIERE	QUE	7054096	-70.03	47.35	31	10.9	11.7	-0.8	1
590	1920-11-13	LA POCATIERE	QUE	7054096	-70.03	47.35	31	-8.8	-7.8	-1	1
591	1920-11-14	LA POCATIERE	QUE	7054096	-70.03	47.35	31	-1.2	-1.1	-0.1	1
592	1920-11-18	LA POCATIERE	QUE	7054096	-70.03	47.35	31	-2.4	-2.2	-0.2	1
593	1921-01-01	LA POCATIERE	QUE	7054096	-70.03	47.35	31	-13.8	-12.2	-1.6	1
594	1921-01-05	LA POCATIERE	QUE	7054096	-70.03	47.35	31	-9.6	-9.4	-0.2	1
595	1921-01-07	LA POCATIERE	QUE	7054096	-70.03	47.35	31	-16	-15.6	-0.4	1
596	1921-01-12	LA POCATIERE	QUE	7054096	-70.03	47.35	31	-16	-15.6	-0.4	1
597	1921-01-13	LA POCATIERE	QUE	7054096	-70.03	47.35	31	-19.3	-17.8	-1.5	1
598	1921-01-14	LA POCATIERE	QUE	7054096	-70.03	47.35	31	-11.4	-10	-1.4	1
599	1921-01-15	LA POCATIERE	QUE	7054096	-70.03	47.35	31	-9.5	-8.9	-0.6	1
600	1921-01-18	LA POCATIERE	QUE	7054096	-70.03	47.35	31	-23.2	-22.2	-1	1
601	1921-01-19	LA POCATIERE	QUE	7054096	-70.03	47.35	31	-22.6	-22.2	-0.4	1
602	1921-01-24	LA POCATIERE	QUE	7054096	-70.03	47.35	31	-16.5	-16.1	-0.4	1
603	1921-01-25	LA POCATIERE	QUE	7054096	-70.03	47.35	31	-20.4	-19.4	-1	1
604	1921-01-26	LA POCATIERE	QUE	7054096	-70.03	47.35	31	-21	-18.9	-2.1	1
605	1921-01-29	LA POCATIERE	QUE	7054096	-70.03	47.35	31	-6.3	-6.1	-0.2	1
606	1921-01-31	LA POCATIERE	QUE	7054096	-70.03	47.35	31	-8.7	-7.8	-0.9	1
607	1922-01-19	LA POCATIERE	QUE	7054096	-70.03	47.35	31	-9.5	-9.4	-0.1	1
608	1923-01-08	LA POCATIERE	QUE	7054096	-70.03	47.35	31	-12.6	-10	-2.6	1
609	1923-01-09	LA POCATIERE	QUE	7054096	-70.03	47.35	31	-12	-11.7	-0.3	1
610	1923-01-23	LA POCATIERE	QUE	7054096	-70.03	47.35	31	-12	-11.7	-0.3	1
611	1923-04-08	LA POCATIERE	QUE	7054096	-70.03	47.35	31	-12	-11.1	-0.9	1

612	1923-12-28	LA POCATIERE	QUE	7054096	-70.03	47.35	31	-8.8	-7.2	-1.6	1
613	1923-12-31	LA POCATIERE	QUE	7054096	-70.03	47.35	31	-15.4	-13.3	-2.1	1
614	1924-02-01	LA POCATIERE	QUE	7054096	-70.03	47.35	31	-12.6	-10	-2.6	1
615	1924-02-05	LA POCATIERE	QUE	7054096	-70.03	47.35	31	-15.4	-14.4	-1	1
616	1924-02-06	LA POCATIERE	QUE	7054096	-70.03	47.35	31	-13.2	-10.6	-2.6	1
617	1924-02-10	LA POCATIERE	QUE	7054096	-70.03	47.35	31	-10.2	-9.4	-0.8	1
618	1924-03-11	LA POCATIERE	QUE	7054096	-70.03	47.35	31	-2.5	-2.2	-0.3	1
619	1924-03-12	LA POCATIERE	QUE	7054096	-70.03	47.35	31	-4	-2.8	-1.2	1
620	1924-12-15	LA POCATIERE	QUE	7054096	-70.03	47.35	31	-20.4	-20	-0.4	1
621	1924-12-16	LA POCATIERE	QUE	7054096	-70.03	47.35	31	-19.9	-19.4	-0.5	1
622	1924-12-18	LA POCATIERE	QUE	7054096	-70.03	47.35	31	-15.4	-12.8	-2.6	1
623	1925-01-02	LA POCATIERE	QUE	7054096	-70.03	47.35	31	-15.4	-13.3	-2.1	1
624	1925-02-14	LA POCATIERE	QUE	7054096	-70.03	47.35	31	-10.8	-9.4	-1.4	1
625	1925-02-15	LA POCATIERE	QUE	7054096	-70.03	47.35	31	-9.5	-8.9	-0.6	1
626	1925-03-17	LA POCATIERE	QUE	7054096	-70.03	47.35	31	2	2.2	-0.2	1
627	1925-11-27	LA POCATIERE	QUE	7054096	-70.03	47.35	31	-9.6	-8.3	-1.3	1
628	1925-12-12	LA POCATIERE	QUE	7054096	-70.03	47.35	31	-12.6	-11.1	-1.5	1
629	1926-01-24	LA POCATIERE	QUE	7054096	-70.03	47.35	31	-13.8	-12.8	-1	1
630	1926-01-25	LA POCATIERE	QUE	7054096	-70.03	47.35	31	-17.6	-16.7	-0.9	1
631	1926-02-01	LA POCATIERE	QUE	7054096	-70.03	47.35	31	-16.5	-15	-1.5	1
632	1926-02-04	LA POCATIERE	QUE	7054096	-70.03	47.35	31	-11.4	-11.1	-0.3	1
633	1927-01-01	LA POCATIERE	QUE	7054096	-70.03	47.35	31	-10.8	-10	-0.8	1
634	1927-01-15	LA POCATIERE	QUE	7054096	-70.03	47.35	31	-14.3	-13.3	-1	1
635	1928-02-19	LA POCATIERE	QUE	7054096	-70.03	47.35	31	-12	-9.4	-2.6	1
636	1928-03-27	LA POCATIERE	QUE	7054096	-70.03	47.35	31	-9.5	-7.8	-1.7	1
637	1928-04-25	LA POCATIERE	QUE	7054096	-70.03	47.35	31	1.6	1.7	-0.1	1
638	1929-01-16	LA POCATIERE	QUE	7054096	-70.03	47.35	31	-20.4	-20	-0.4	1
639	1929-01-23	LA POCATIERE	QUE	7054096	-70.03	47.35	31	-21.5	-20.6	-0.9	1
640	1929-10-04	LA POCATIERE	QUE	7054096	-70.03	47.35	31	3.3	4.4	-1.1	1
641	1929-10-05	LA POCATIERE	QUE	7054096	-70.03	47.35	31	3.3	4.4	-1.1	1
642	1929-12-06	LA POCATIERE	QUE	7054096	-70.03	47.35	31	-17.1	-16.7	-0.4	1
643	1929-12-07	LA POCATIERE	QUE	7054096	-70.03	47.35	31	-17.1	-16.7	-0.4	1
644	1930-01-09	LA POCATIERE	QUE	7054096	-70.03	47.35	31	-15.4	-14.4	-1	1
645	1930-07-30	LA POCATIERE	QUE	7054096	-70.03	47.35	31	10	10.6	-0.6	1

646	1931-12-14	LA POCATIERE	QUE	7054096	-70.03	47.35	31	-4.8	-4.4	-0.4	1
647	1932-02-29	LA POCATIERE	QUE	7054096	-70.03	47.35	31	-8	-7.8	-0.2	1
648	1934-11-11	LA POCATIERE	QUE	7054096	-70.03	47.35	31	-2.3	-2.2	-0.1	1
649	1935-12-24	LA POCATIERE	QUE	7054096	-70.03	47.35	31	-14.3	-13.9	-0.4	1
650	1935-12-26	LA POCATIERE	QUE	7054096	-70.03	47.35	31	-14.3	-13.9	-0.4	1
651	1936-02-17	LA POCATIERE	QUE	7054096	-70.03	47.35	31	-6.4	-5.6	-0.8	1
652	1936-02-23	LA POCATIERE	QUE	7054096	-70.03	47.35	31	-10.2	-9.4	-0.8	1
653	1939-09-11	LA POCATIERE	QUE	7054096	-70.03	47.35	31	14.7	15	-0.3	1
654	1939-12-11	LA POCATIERE	QUE	7054096	-70.03	47.35	31	-11.7	-11.1	-0.6	1
655	1939-12-23	LA POCATIERE	QUE	7054096	-70.03	47.35	31	-9.6	-8.3	-1.3	1
656	1940-01-16	LA POCATIERE	QUE	7054096	-70.03	47.35	31	-13.8	-12.2	-1.6	1
657	1940-12-13	LA POCATIERE	QUE	7054096	-70.03	47.35	31	-11.2	-10	-1.2	1
658	1941-01-05	LA POCATIERE	QUE	7054096	-70.03	47.35	31	-2.9	-2.8	-0.1	1
659	1941-01-13	LA POCATIERE	QUE	7054096	-70.03	47.35	31	-13.8	-12.2	-1.6	1
660	1941-02-09	LA POCATIERE	QUE	7054096	-70.03	47.35	31	-12.2	-10.6	-1.6	1
661	1941-03-18	LA POCATIERE	QUE	7054096	-70.03	47.35	31	-14.3	-13.9	-0.4	1
662	1941-10-28	LA POCATIERE	QUE	7054096	-70.03	47.35	31	3	3.3	-0.3	1
663	1941-11-27	LA POCATIERE	QUE	7054096	-70.03	47.35	31	-8	-6.1	-1.9	1
664	1941-12-07	LA POCATIERE	QUE	7054096	-70.03	47.35	31	-6.4	-5	-1.4	1
665	1941-12-17	LA POCATIERE	QUE	7054096	-70.03	47.35	31	-8.5	-8.3	-0.2	1
666	1942-02-02	LA POCATIERE	QUE	7054096	-70.03	47.35	31	-12.2	-11.7	-0.5	1
667	1942-02-09	LA POCATIERE	QUE	7054096	-70.03	47.35	31	-11.2	-10	-1.2	1
668	1942-03-10	LA POCATIERE	QUE	7054096	-70.03	47.35	31	-7.9	-5.6	-2.3	1
669	1942-04-20	LA POCATIERE	QUE	7054096	-70.03	47.35	31	-0.1	0	-0.1	1
670	1942-09-10	LA POCATIERE	QUE	7054096	-70.03	47.35	31	12.1	12.2	-0.1	1
671	1942-11-14	LA POCATIERE	QUE	7054096	-70.03	47.35	31	-3.5	-3.3	-0.2	1
672	1942-12-03	LA POCATIERE	QUE	7054096	-70.03	47.35	31	-7.8	-6.1	-1.7	1
673	1942-12-11	LA POCATIERE	QUE	7054096	-70.03	47.35	31	-10.7	-9.4	-1.3	1
674	1942-12-14	LA POCATIERE	QUE	7054096	-70.03	47.35	31	-14.3	-13.9	-0.4	1
675	1942-12-25	LA POCATIERE	QUE	7054096	-70.03	47.35	31	-5.7	-5.6	-0.1	1
676	1943-01-13	LA POCATIERE	QUE	7054096	-70.03	47.35	31	-9.6	-7.8	-1.8	1
677	1943-01-20	LA POCATIERE	QUE	7054096	-70.03	47.35	31	-24.2	-22.8	-1.4	1
678	1943-02-02	LA POCATIERE	QUE	7054096	-70.03	47.35	31	-7.2	-6.1	-1.1	1
679	1943-02-08	LA POCATIERE	QUE	7054096	-70.03	47.35	31	-6.4	-4.4	-2	1

680	1943-02-12	LA POCATIERE	QUE	7054096	-70.03	47.35	31	-9.1	-8.3	-0.8	1
681	1943-03-02	LA POCATIERE	QUE	7054096	-70.03	47.35	31	-12.2	-11.7	-0.5	1
682	1943-03-03	LA POCATIERE	QUE	7054096	-70.03	47.35	31	-16.4	-15.6	-0.8	1
683	1943-10-02	LA POCATIERE	QUE	7054096	-70.03	47.35	31	8.6	9.4	-0.8	1
684	1943-11-03	LA POCATIERE	QUE	7054096	-70.03	47.35	31	1.9	2.8	-0.9	1
685	1943-12-10	LA POCATIERE	QUE	7054096	-70.03	47.35	31	-5.7	-5	-0.7	1
686	1943-12-11	LA POCATIERE	QUE	7054096	-70.03	47.35	31	-11.7	-11.1	-0.6	1
687	1943-12-13	LA POCATIERE	QUE	7054096	-70.03	47.35	31	-16.4	-16.1	-0.3	1
688	1943-12-28	LA POCATIERE	QUE	7054096	-70.03	47.35	31	-13.2	-11.1	-2.1	1
689	1944-01-08	LA POCATIERE	QUE	7054096	-70.03	47.35	31	-14.8	-13.3	-1.5	1
690	1944-03-01	LA POCATIERE	QUE	7054096	-70.03	47.35	31	-9.1	-8.3	-0.8	1
691	1944-03-09	LA POCATIERE	QUE	7054096	-70.03	47.35	31	-10.2	-8.3	-1.9	1
692	1944-03-18	LA POCATIERE	QUE	7054096	-70.03	47.35	31	-5.9	-3.9	-2	1
693	1944-11-05	LA POCATIERE	QUE	7054096	-70.03	47.35	31	4.9	5.6	-0.7	1
694	1944-11-06	LA POCATIERE	QUE	7054096	-70.03	47.35	31	-1.1	0	-1.1	1
695	1944-11-11	LA POCATIERE	QUE	7054096	-70.03	47.35	31	3.1	3.3	-0.2	1
696	1944-12-26	LA POCATIERE	QUE	7054096	-70.03	47.35	31	-10.2	-9.4	-0.8	1
697	1945-01-05	LA POCATIERE	QUE	7054096	-70.03	47.35	31	-13.8	-12.2	-1.6	1
698	1945-01-06	LA POCATIERE	QUE	7054096	-70.03	47.35	31	-23.1	-22.2	-0.9	1
699	1945-01-10	LA POCATIERE	QUE	7054096	-70.03	47.35	31	-22.6	-22.2	-0.4	1
700	1945-01-18	LA POCATIERE	QUE	7054096	-70.03	47.35	31	-13.8	-13.3	-0.5	1
701	1945-02-17	LA POCATIERE	QUE	7054096	-70.03	47.35	31	-7.9	-7.2	-0.7	1
702	1945-02-24	LA POCATIERE	QUE	7054096	-70.03	47.35	31	-5.1	-3.9	-1.2	1
703	1945-05-18	LA POCATIERE	QUE	7054096	-70.03	47.35	31	4.9	5	-0.1	1
704	1945-05-23	LA POCATIERE	QUE	7054096	-70.03	47.35	31	9.7	10.6	-0.9	1
705	1945-10-03	LA POCATIERE	QUE	7054096	-70.03	47.35	31	3	3.3	-0.3	1
706	1945-11-25	LA POCATIERE	QUE	7054096	-70.03	47.35	31	-5.8	-5.6	-0.2	1
707	1945-12-09	LA POCATIERE	QUE	7054096	-70.03	47.35	31	-1.7	-1.1	-0.6	1
708	1945-12-11	LA POCATIERE	QUE	7054096	-70.03	47.35	31	-10.7	-8.9	-1.8	1
709	1945-12-12	LA POCATIERE	QUE	7054096	-70.03	47.35	31	-17	-16.1	-0.9	1
710	1945-12-16	LA POCATIERE	QUE	7054096	-70.03	47.35	31	-8.5	-7.8	-0.7	1
711	1945-12-17	LA POCATIERE	QUE	7054096	-70.03	47.35	31	-12.8	-11.1	-1.7	1
712	1945-12-21	LA POCATIERE	QUE	7054096	-70.03	47.35	31	-17.6	-15.6	-2	1
713	1945-12-31	LA POCATIERE	QUE	7054096	-70.03	47.35	31	-5.7	-3.9	-1.8	1

714	1946-01-01	LA POCATIERE	QUE	7054096	-70.03	47.35	31	-7.9	-6.7	-1.2	1
715	1946-01-02	LA POCATIERE	QUE	7054096	-70.03	47.35	31	-17.6	-16.7	-0.9	1
716	1946-01-13	LA POCATIERE	QUE	7054096	-70.03	47.35	31	-8.5	-6.7	-1.8	1
717	1946-02-18	LA POCATIERE	QUE	7054096	-70.03	47.35	31	-14.3	-13.9	-0.4	1
718	1946-11-23	LA POCATIERE	QUE	7054096	-70.03	47.35	31	-4.9	-4.4	-0.5	1
719	1946-11-28	LA POCATIERE	QUE	7054096	-70.03	47.35	31	-7.9	-7.2	-0.7	1
720	1946-12-02	LA POCATIERE	QUE	7054096	-70.03	47.35	31	-13.8	-12.8	-1	1
721	1947-02-09	LA POCATIERE	QUE	7054096	-70.03	47.35	31	-11.2	-11.1	-0.1	1
722	1947-03-15	LA POCATIERE	QUE	7054096	-70.03	47.35	31	-3.5	-3.3	-0.2	1
723	1947-11-13	LA POCATIERE	QUE	7054096	-70.03	47.35	31	-0.1	0	-0.1	1
724	1947-11-27	LA POCATIERE	QUE	7054096	-70.03	47.35	31	-9.1	-8.3	-0.8	1
725	1947-12-17	LA POCATIERE	QUE	7054096	-70.03	47.35	31	-9.1	-8.3	-0.8	1
726	1947-12-29	LA POCATIERE	QUE	7054096	-70.03	47.35	31	-11.3	-10	-1.3	1
727	1948-01-10	LA POCATIERE	QUE	7054096	-70.03	47.35	31	-11.7	-10	-1.7	1
728	1948-01-18	LA POCATIERE	QUE	7054096	-70.03	47.35	31	-12.8	-12.2	-0.6	1
729	1948-01-23	LA POCATIERE	QUE	7054096	-70.03	47.35	31	-20.9	-20.6	-0.3	1
730	1948-02-18	LA POCATIERE	QUE	7054096	-70.03	47.35	31	-10.7	-8.9	-1.8	1
731	1948-05-18	LA POCATIERE	QUE	7054096	-70.03	47.35	31	4.9	5	-0.1	1
732	1948-12-10	LA POCATIERE	QUE	7054096	-70.03	47.35	31	-2.2	-1.7	-0.5	1
733	1949-01-20	LA POCATIERE	QUE	7054096	-70.03	47.35	31	-13.2	-11.7	-1.5	1
734	1949-02-11	LA POCATIERE	QUE	7054096	-70.03	47.35	31	-20.3	-19.4	-0.9	1
735	1949-03-11	LA POCATIERE	QUE	7054096	-70.03	47.35	31	-4.9	-4.4	-0.5	1
736	1949-11-26	LA POCATIERE	QUE	7054096	-70.03	47.35	31	-9.6	-9.4	-0.2	1
737	1949-12-06	LA POCATIERE	QUE	7054096	-70.03	47.35	31	-8.5	-7.2	-1.3	1
738	1949-12-13	LA POCATIERE	QUE	7054096	-70.03	47.35	31	1.9	2.8	-0.9	1
739	1949-12-29	LA POCATIERE	QUE	7054096	-70.03	47.35	31	-12.8	-11.7	-1.1	1
740	1949-12-30	LA POCATIERE	QUE	7054096	-70.03	47.35	31	-13.2	-12.8	-0.4	1
741	1950-01-23	LA POCATIERE	QUE	7054096	-70.03	47.35	31	-13.2	-12.8	-0.4	1
742	1950-01-27	LA POCATIERE	QUE	7054096	-70.03	47.35	31	-13.2	-12.2	-1	1
743	1950-02-20	LA POCATIERE	QUE	7054096	-70.03	47.35	31	-19.8	-18.9	-0.9	1
744	1950-06-17	LA POCATIERE	QUE	7054096	-70.03	47.35	31	15.9	16.7	-0.8	1
745	1950-09-19	LA POCATIERE	QUE	7054096	-70.03	47.35	31	11.5	11.7	-0.2	1
746	1950-11-21	LA POCATIERE	QUE	7054096	-70.03	47.35	31	-0.6	0	-0.6	1
747	1950-11-28	LA POCATIERE	QUE	7054096	-70.03	47.35	31	1.9	2.2	-0.3	1

748	1950-12-01	LA POCATIERE	QUE	7054096	-70.03	47.35	31	0.5	0.6	-0.1	1
749	1950-12-19	LA POCATIERE	QUE	7054096	-70.03	47.35	31	-11.3	-10	-1.3	1
750	1950-12-26	LA POCATIERE	QUE	7054096	-70.03	47.35	31	-25.3	-23.3	-2	1
751	1951-01-12	LA POCATIERE	QUE	7054096	-70.03	47.35	31	-2.9	-2.2	-0.7	1
752	1951-01-22	LA POCATIERE	QUE	7054096	-70.03	47.35	31	-24.8	-23.3	-1.5	1
753	1951-01-30	LA POCATIERE	QUE	7054096	-70.03	47.35	31	-24.8	-23.3	-1.5	1
754	1951-02-08	LA POCATIERE	QUE	7054096	-70.03	47.35	31	-17	-15.6	-1.4	1
755	1951-02-28	LA POCATIERE	QUE	7054096	-70.03	47.35	31	-10.7	-10.6	-0.1	1
756	1951-08-17	LA POCATIERE	QUE	7054096	-70.03	47.35	31	9.7	10	-0.3	1
757	1951-10-24	LA POCATIERE	QUE	7054096	-70.03	47.35	31	3.7	4.4	-0.7	1
758	1951-11-17	LA POCATIERE	QUE	7054096	-70.03	47.35	31	-2.3	-1.7	-0.6	1
759	1951-11-18	LA POCATIERE	QUE	7054096	-70.03	47.35	31	-4.2	-3.9	-0.3	1
760	1951-11-27	LA POCATIERE	QUE	7054096	-70.03	47.35	31	-10.7	-9.4	-1.3	1
761	1951-12-13	LA POCATIERE	QUE	7054096	-70.03	47.35	31	-17.6	-17.2	-0.4	1
762	1952-01-21	LA POCATIERE	QUE	7054096	-70.03	47.35	31	-14.8	-13.9	-0.9	1
763	1952-01-28	LA POCATIERE	QUE	7054096	-70.03	47.35	31	-12.8	-11.7	-1.1	1
764	1952-10-06	LA POCATIERE	QUE	7054096	-70.03	47.35	31	4.9	5.6	-0.7	1
765	1979-07-01	DAWSON	YT	2100LRP	-139.13	64.05	370	2.2	6.1	-3.9	1
766	1995-01-23	WATSON LAKE	YT	2101204	-128.82	60.12	683	-18.8	-17.1	-1.7	1
767	2005-03-30	CORAL HARBOUR	NU	2301000	-83.37	64.2	62	-12.6	-9.1	-3.5	1
768	1933-11-30	CHURCHILL	MAN	5060595	-94.05	58.73	29	-30.3	-30	-0.3	1
769	1935-01-17	CHURCHILL	MAN	5060595	-94.05	58.73	29	-39	-38.9	-0.1	1
770	1936-01-31	CHURCHILL	MAN	5060595	-94.05	58.73	29	-38.4	-38.3	-0.1	1
771	1936-02-01	CHURCHILL	MAN	5060595	-94.05	58.73	29	-42.3	-41.7	-0.6	1
772	1939-01-30	CHURCHILL	MAN	5060595	-94.05	58.73	29	-33.4	-33.3	-0.1	1
773	1946-02-06	CHURCHILL	MAN	5060595	-94.05	58.73	29	-32.3	-32.2	-0.1	1
774	1994-01-11	CHURCHILL	MAN	5060595	-94.05	58.73	29	-36.7	-36.5	-0.2	1
775	1997-01-06	CHURCHILL	MAN	5060595	-94.05	58.73	29	-34.7	-33.3	-1.4	1
776	2011-01-29	CHURCHILL	MAN	5060595	-94.05	58.73	29	-31.2	-24.1	-7.1	1
777	2013-08-18	CHURCHILL	MAN	5060595	-94.05	58.73	29	12.3	14	-1.7	1
778	2008-12-19	SALMON ARM	BC	1167337	-119.23	50.68	419	-23	-18	-5	1
779	2011-05-26	SALMON ARM	BC	1167337	-119.23	50.68	419	7	8	-1	1
780	1886-01-16	PRINCE ALBERT	SASK	4056241	-105.67	53.22	428	-27.3	-27	-0.3	1
781	1911-04-28	THE PAS	MAN	5052881	-101.1	53.97	271	1.4	1.5	-0.1	1

782	1911-11-09	THE PAS	MAN	5052881	-101.1	53.97	271	-11.2	-9.5	-1.7	1
783	1911-11-21	THE PAS	MAN	5052881	-101.1	53.97	271	-9.2	-9	-0.2	1
784	1911-11-27	THE PAS	MAN	5052881	-101.1	53.97	271	-15.1	-14.3	-0.8	1
785	1911-12-13	THE PAS	MAN	5052881	-101.1	53.97	271	-11.2	-9.5	-1.7	1
786	1911-12-15	THE PAS	MAN	5052881	-101.1	53.97	271	-11.8	-11.3	-0.5	1
787	1911-12-17	THE PAS	MAN	5052881	-101.1	53.97	271	-13.7	-13.6	-0.1	1
788	1912-01-31	THE PAS	MAN	5052881	-101.1	53.97	271	-11.3	-9	-2.3	1
789	1912-09-13	THE PAS	MAN	5052881	-101.1	53.97	271	7.7	8.7	-1	1
790	1912-12-17	THE PAS	MAN	5052881	-101.1	53.97	271	-8	-7.8	-0.2	1
791	1912-12-31	THE PAS	MAN	5052881	-101.1	53.97	271	-13.7	-12.9	-0.8	1
792	1914-12-02	THE PAS	MAN	5052881	-101.1	53.97	271	-12.5	-11.8	-0.7	1
793	1914-12-06	THE PAS	MAN	5052881	-101.1	53.97	271	-10.3	-8.6	-1.7	1
794	1914-12-11	THE PAS	MAN	5052881	-101.1	53.97	271	-12.1	-11.3	-0.8	1
795	1915-11-12	THE PAS	MAN	5052881	-101.1	53.97	271	-9.2	-9	-0.2	1
796	1918-01-19	THE PAS	MAN	5052881	-101.1	53.97	271	-12.9	-11.8	-1.1	1
797	1919-10-29	THE PAS	MAN	5052881	-101.1	53.97	271	-9.2	-8.9	-0.3	1
798	1919-11-08	THE PAS	MAN	5052881	-101.1	53.97	271	-11.2	-10.7	-0.5	1
799	1919-12-27	THE PAS	MAN	5052881	-101.1	53.97	271	-11.3	-9.9	-1.4	1
800	1921-12-01	THE PAS	MAN	5052881	-101.1	53.97	271	-6.7	-6.5	-0.2	1
801	1924-11-09	THE PAS	MAN	5052881	-101.1	53.97	271	-10.8	-10.7	-0.1	1
802	1925-10-28	THE PAS	MAN	5052881	-101.1	53.97	271	-12.1	-10.7	-1.4	1
803	1925-12-29	THE PAS	MAN	5052881	-101.1	53.97	271	-11.2	-10.8	-0.4	1
804	1926-01-04	THE PAS	MAN	5052881	-101.1	53.97	271	-12.9	-12.4	-0.5	1
805	1929-09-02	THE PAS	MAN	5052881	-101.1	53.97	271	8.4	8.7	-0.3	1
806	1933-02-19	THE PAS	MAN	5052881	-101.1	53.97	271	-13	-11.8	-1.2	1
807	1933-03-13	THE PAS	MAN	5052881	-101.1	53.97	271	-12.6	-12.4	-0.2	1
808	1934-11-27	THE PAS	MAN	5052881	-101.1	53.97	271	-10.3	-9.1	-1.2	1
809	1934-12-08	THE PAS	MAN	5052881	-101.1	53.97	271	-6.7	-5.8	-0.9	1
810	1937-11-15	THE PAS	MAN	5052881	-101.1	53.97	271	-11.7	-10.8	-0.9	1
811	1937-11-26	THE PAS	MAN	5052881	-101.1	53.97	271	-16	-15.6	-0.4	1
812	1939-12-27	THE PAS	MAN	5052881	-101.1	53.97	271	-22.6	-22	-0.6	1
813	1940-11-07	THE PAS	MAN	5052881	-101.1	53.97	271	-14.2	-13.6	-0.6	1
814	1940-12-06	THE PAS	MAN	5052881	-101.1	53.97	271	-15.6	-15.5	-0.1	1
815	1941-12-09	THE PAS	MAN	5052881	-101.1	53.97	271	-20.3	-20.1	-0.2	1

816	1944-02-23	THE PAS	MAN	5052881	-101.1	53.97	271	-12.5	-12.4	-0.1	1
817	1944-12-07	THE PAS	MAN	5052881	-101.1	53.97	271	-8.6	-7.7	-0.9	1
818	1944-12-08	THE PAS	MAN	5052881	-101.1	53.97	271	-8.6	-7.7	-0.9	1
819	1945-11-26	THE PAS	MAN	5052881	-101.1	53.97	271	-8.6	-8.2	-0.4	1
820	1946-01-03	THE PAS	MAN	5052881	-101.1	53.97	271	-9.2	-8.3	-0.9	1
821	1946-03-03	THE PAS	MAN	5052881	-101.1	53.97	271	-14.6	-12.9	-1.7	1
822	1978-10-28	HALL BEACH	NU	2402354	-81.25	68.78	9	-29.3	-28.2	-1.1	1
823	2007-03-04	HALL BEACH	NU	2402354	-81.25	68.78	9	-40.9	-38.2	-2.7	1
824	2015-09-25	HALL BEACH	NU	2402354	-81.25	68.78	9	0.1	1	-0.9	1
825	2015-09-26	HALL BEACH	NU	2402354	-81.25	68.78	9	1.2	1.4	-0.2	1
826	1944-12-24	WHITECOURT	ALTA	3067373	-115.78	54.15	782	-9.4	-9.3	-0.1	1
827	1946-01-28	WHITECOURT	ALTA	3067373	-115.78	54.15	782	-16.7	-16.6	-0.1	1
828	1946-11-27	WHITECOURT	ALTA	3067373	-115.78	54.15	782	-15	-14.6	-0.4	1
829	1949-01-31	WHITECOURT	ALTA	3067373	-115.78	54.15	782	-11.1	-9.8	-1.3	1
830	1950-11-16	WHITECOURT	ALTA	3067373	-115.78	54.15	782	-15	-14.7	-0.3	1
831	1950-12-20	WHITECOURT	ALTA	3067373	-115.78	54.15	782	-11.7	-11.2	-0.5	1
832	1951-05-02	WHITECOURT	ALTA	3067373	-115.78	54.15	782	2.2	2.4	-0.2	1
833	1953-01-11	WHITECOURT	ALTA	3067373	-115.78	54.15	782	-25.6	-25.5	-0.1	1
834	1954-11-13	WHITECOURT	ALTA	3067373	-115.78	54.15	782	-7.8	-7.7	-0.1	1
835	1960-01-07	WHITECOURT	ALTA	3067373	-115.78	54.15	782	-2.8	-2.7	-0.1	1
836	1960-01-25	WHITECOURT	ALTA	3067373	-115.78	54.15	782	-17.8	-17.3	-0.5	1
837	1960-03-09	WHITECOURT	ALTA	3067373	-115.78	54.15	782	-11.7	-11.3	-0.4	1
838	1964-11-30	WHITECOURT	ALTA	3067373	-115.78	54.15	782	-21.7	-21.4	-0.3	1
839	1965-01-03	WHITECOURT	ALTA	3067373	-115.78	54.15	782	-31.1	-30.8	-0.3	1
840	1965-11-18	WHITECOURT	ALTA	3067373	-115.78	54.15	782	-5.6	-5.3	-0.3	1
841	1971-12-22	WHITECOURT	ALTA	3067373	-115.78	54.15	782	-25.6	-25.5	-0.1	1
842	1972-11-13	WHITECOURT	ALTA	3067373	-115.78	54.15	782	-2.2	-2	-0.2	1
843	1974-01-14	WHITECOURT	ALTA	3067373	-115.78	54.15	782	-26.7	-26.5	-0.2	1
844	1997-10-11	WHITECOURT	ALTA	3067373	-115.78	54.15	782	-1.5	-1.2	-0.3	1
845	2012-10-19	WHITECOURT	ALTA	3067373	-115.78	54.15	782	0.6	0.8	-0.2	1
846	2014-01-22	WHITECOURT	ALTA	3067373	-115.78	54.15	782	-3.8	-2.2	-1.6	1
847	2008-01-28	HUDSON BAY	SASK	4083324	-102.32	52.82	358	-24.5	-21	-3.5	1
848	1915-09-08	INDIAN BAY	MAN	5031320	-95.2	49.62	327	15.6	15.8	-0.2	1
849	1915-11-11	INDIAN BAY	MAN	5031320	-95.2	49.62	327	-1.1	-0.9	-0.2	1

850	1915-12-11	INDIAN BAY	MAN	5031320	-95.2	49.62	327	-11.7	-11.6	-0.1	1
851	1916-01-10	INDIAN BAY	MAN	5031320	-95.2	49.62	327	-19.4	-18.5	-0.9	1
852	1917-09-25	INDIAN BAY	MAN	5031320	-95.2	49.62	327	15	15.7	-0.7	1
853	1917-10-17	INDIAN BAY	MAN	5031320	-95.2	49.62	327	2.2	2.5	-0.3	1
854	1918-01-11	INDIAN BAY	MAN	5031320	-95.2	49.62	327	-22.8	-21.8	-1	1
855	1918-09-01	INDIAN BAY	MAN	5031320	-95.2	49.62	327	22.2	22.3	-0.1	1
856	1918-11-06	INDIAN BAY	MAN	5031320	-95.2	49.62	327	1.1	1.6	-0.5	1
857	1921-02-16	INDIAN BAY	MAN	5031320	-95.2	49.62	327	-13.3	-13.2	-0.1	1
858	1921-12-19	INDIAN BAY	MAN	5031320	-95.2	49.62	327	-19.4	-19	-0.4	1
859	1922-01-03	INDIAN BAY	MAN	5031320	-95.2	49.62	327	-16.1	-16	-0.1	1
860	1922-12-11	INDIAN BAY	MAN	5031320	-95.2	49.62	327	-17.8	-17.3	-0.5	1
861	1925-11-05	INDIAN BAY	MAN	5031320	-95.2	49.62	327	-12.2	-12.1	-0.1	1
862	1926-07-08	INDIAN BAY	MAN	5031320	-95.2	49.62	327	19.4	19.5	-0.1	1
863	1927-01-17	INDIAN BAY	MAN	5031320	-95.2	49.62	327	-24.4	-24.2	-0.2	1
864	1928-10-11	INDIAN BAY	MAN	5031320	-95.2	49.62	327	3.9	4.3	-0.4	1
865	1929-01-22	INDIAN BAY	MAN	5031320	-95.2	49.62	327	-19.4	-18.9	-0.5	1
866	1929-03-06	INDIAN BAY	MAN	5031320	-95.2	49.62	327	-17.2	-16.9	-0.3	1
867	1932-01-29	INDIAN BAY	MAN	5031320	-95.2	49.62	327	-22.2	-21.7	-0.5	1
868	1933-12-10	INDIAN BAY	MAN	5031320	-95.2	49.62	327	-22.2	-21.3	-0.9	1
869	1933-12-31	INDIAN BAY	MAN	5031320	-95.2	49.62	327	-25	-23	-2	1
870	1936-01-04	INDIAN BAY	MAN	5031320	-95.2	49.62	327	-13.9	-13.7	-0.2	1
871	1936-12-31	INDIAN BAY	MAN	5031320	-95.2	49.62	327	-19.4	-18.9	-0.5	1
872	1937-07-15	INDIAN BAY	MAN	5031320	-95.2	49.62	327	18.3	18.4	-0.1	1
873	1938-12-16	INDIAN BAY	MAN	5031320	-95.2	49.62	327	-11.7	-11.5	-0.2	1
874	1942-02-16	INDIAN BAY	MAN	5031320	-95.2	49.62	327	-19.4	-19	-0.4	1
875	1943-05-06	INDIAN BAY	MAN	5031320	-95.2	49.62	327	3.3	3.8	-0.5	1
876	1944-12-20	INDIAN BAY	MAN	5031320	-95.2	49.62	327	-20.6	-19.8	-0.8	1
877	1946-02-06	INDIAN BAY	MAN	5031320	-95.2	49.62	327	-20.6	-19.3	-1.3	1
878	1946-05-03	INDIAN BAY	MAN	5031320	-95.2	49.62	327	9.4	9.6	-0.2	1
879	1946-12-28	INDIAN BAY	MAN	5031320	-95.2	49.62	327	-20	-19.7	-0.3	1
880	1947-01-05	INDIAN BAY	MAN	5031320	-95.2	49.62	327	-7.8	-6.6	-1.2	1
881	1949-07-06	INDIAN BAY	MAN	5031320	-95.2	49.62	327	18.3	18.4	-0.1	1
882	1949-12-12	INDIAN BAY	MAN	5031320	-95.2	49.62	327	-20	-19.3	-0.7	1
883	1951-08-25	INDIAN BAY	MAN	5031320	-95.2	49.62	327	18.9	19	-0.1	1

884	1953-08-01	INDIAN BAY	MAN	5031320	-95.2	49.62	327	18.3	18.5	-0.2	1
885	1953-12-02	INDIAN BAY	MAN	5031320	-95.2	49.62	327	-3.9	-3.4	-0.5	1
886	1954-01-14	INDIAN BAY	MAN	5031320	-95.2	49.62	327	-15.6	-15.2	-0.4	1
887	1954-07-17	INDIAN BAY	MAN	5031320	-95.2	49.62	327	22.2	22.4	-0.2	1
888	1954-12-30	INDIAN BAY	MAN	5031320	-95.2	49.62	327	-18.9	-18.6	-0.3	1
889	1955-08-15	INDIAN BAY	MAN	5031320	-95.2	49.62	327	17.8	19	-1.2	1
890	1955-11-23	INDIAN BAY	MAN	5031320	-95.2	49.62	327	-15.6	-15.3	-0.3	1
891	1955-12-13	INDIAN BAY	MAN	5031320	-95.2	49.62	327	-11.7	-11.5	-0.2	1
892	1956-09-13	INDIAN BAY	MAN	5031320	-95.2	49.62	327	10	10.3	-0.3	1
893	1956-11-05	INDIAN BAY	MAN	5031320	-95.2	49.62	327	5.6	5.8	-0.2	1
894	1956-12-11	INDIAN BAY	MAN	5031320	-95.2	49.62	327	-16.1	-15.3	-0.8	1
895	1957-09-02	INDIAN BAY	MAN	5031320	-95.2	49.62	327	18.9	19	-0.1	1
896	1958-11-26	INDIAN BAY	MAN	5031320	-95.2	49.62	327	-12.2	-11.5	-0.7	1
897	1959-05-26	INDIAN BAY	MAN	5031320	-95.2	49.62	327	12.2	12.7	-0.5	1
898	1960-01-03	INDIAN BAY	MAN	5031320	-95.2	49.62	327	-23.3	-22.1	-1.2	1
899	1961-09-27	INDIAN BAY	MAN	5031320	-95.2	49.62	327	2.8	3.3	-0.5	1
900	1962-01-08	INDIAN BAY	MAN	5031320	-95.2	49.62	327	-21.1	-19.1	-2	1
901	1962-01-16	INDIAN BAY	MAN	5031320	-95.2	49.62	327	-30	-28.2	-1.8	1
902	1962-07-02	INDIAN BAY	MAN	5031320	-95.2	49.62	327	19.4	19.6	-0.2	1
903	1962-08-11	INDIAN BAY	MAN	5031320	-95.2	49.62	327	20	20.1	-0.1	1
904	1964-03-16	INDIAN BAY	MAN	5031320	-95.2	49.62	327	-15	-14.7	-0.3	1
905	1964-12-12	INDIAN BAY	MAN	5031320	-95.2	49.62	327	-5	-4.8	-0.2	1
906	1965-01-08	INDIAN BAY	MAN	5031320	-95.2	49.62	327	-23.9	-22.8	-1.1	1
907	1965-02-21	INDIAN BAY	MAN	5031320	-95.2	49.62	327	-25	-23.9	-1.1	1
908	1966-01-20	INDIAN BAY	MAN	5031320	-95.2	49.62	327	-22.2	-20.6	-1.6	1
909	1966-04-17	INDIAN BAY	MAN	5031320	-95.2	49.62	327	0.6	0.7	-0.1	1
910	1966-12-09	INDIAN BAY	MAN	5031320	-95.2	49.62	327	-17.8	-17.2	-0.6	1
911	1967-08-17	INDIAN BAY	MAN	5031320	-95.2	49.62	327	16.7	17.3	-0.6	1
912	1967-09-13	INDIAN BAY	MAN	5031320	-95.2	49.62	327	17.2	17.3	-0.1	1
913	1967-12-21	INDIAN BAY	MAN	5031320	-95.2	49.62	327	-17.8	-17.1	-0.7	1
914	1968-07-21	INDIAN BAY	MAN	5031320	-95.2	49.62	327	17.8	18.5	-0.7	1
915	1968-08-24	INDIAN BAY	MAN	5031320	-95.2	49.62	327	16.1	16.6	-0.5	1
916	1968-09-17	INDIAN BAY	MAN	5031320	-95.2	49.62	327	14.4	15.3	-0.9	1
917	1968-12-23	INDIAN BAY	MAN	5031320	-95.2	49.62	327	-17.2	-17.1	-0.1	1

918	1969-01-28	INDIAN BAY	MAN	5031320	-95.2	49.62	327	-16.1	-15.3	-0.8	1
919	1969-06-27	INDIAN BAY	MAN	5031320	-95.2	49.62	327	14.4	15.3	-0.9	1
920	1969-10-10	INDIAN BAY	MAN	5031320	-95.2	49.62	327	3.3	3.9	-0.6	1
921	1970-02-24	INDIAN BAY	MAN	5031320	-95.2	49.62	327	-9.4	-9.2	-0.2	1
922	1970-07-18	INDIAN BAY	MAN	5031320	-95.2	49.62	327	17.8	19	-1.2	1
923	1970-09-21	INDIAN BAY	MAN	5031320	-95.2	49.62	327	16.7	17.3	-0.6	1
924	1971-12-16	INDIAN BAY	MAN	5031320	-95.2	49.62	327	-17.8	-16.4	-1.4	1
925	1972-10-16	INDIAN BAY	MAN	5031320	-95.2	49.62	327	0	0.3	-0.3	1
926	1972-10-27	INDIAN BAY	MAN	5031320	-95.2	49.62	327	1.7	2.6	-0.9	1
927	1972-11-27	INDIAN BAY	MAN	5031320	-95.2	49.62	327	-10	-8.8	-1.2	1
928	1972-12-23	INDIAN BAY	MAN	5031320	-95.2	49.62	327	-15.6	-13.5	-2.1	1
929	1972-12-31	INDIAN BAY	MAN	5031320	-95.2	49.62	327	-15.6	-13.5	-2.1	1
930	1973-01-03	INDIAN BAY	MAN	5031320	-95.2	49.62	327	-12.8	-11.3	-1.5	1
931	1973-01-04	INDIAN BAY	MAN	5031320	-95.2	49.62	327	-23.9	-23	-0.9	1
932	1973-02-13	INDIAN BAY	MAN	5031320	-95.2	49.62	327	-14.4	-12.2	-2.2	1
933	1973-04-22	INDIAN BAY	MAN	5031320	-95.2	49.62	327	0.6	1.5	-0.9	1
934	1973-06-26	INDIAN BAY	MAN	5031320	-95.2	49.62	327	21.1	22.1	-1	1
935	1973-12-09	INDIAN BAY	MAN	5031320	-95.2	49.62	327	-13.3	-13.1	-0.2	1
936	1973-12-12	INDIAN BAY	MAN	5031320	-95.2	49.62	327	-15	-14	-1	1
937	1974-12-07	INDIAN BAY	MAN	5031320	-95.2	49.62	327	-12.8	-12.2	-0.6	1
938	1975-01-11	INDIAN BAY	MAN	5031320	-95.2	49.62	327	-19.4	-17	-2.4	1
939	1975-01-12	INDIAN BAY	MAN	5031320	-95.2	49.62	327	-22.8	-21.3	-1.5	1
940	1975-11-22	INDIAN BAY	MAN	5031320	-95.2	49.62	327	-11.7	-10.5	-1.2	1
941	1975-11-30	INDIAN BAY	MAN	5031320	-95.2	49.62	327	-18.3	-16.4	-1.9	1
942	1975-12-05	INDIAN BAY	MAN	5031320	-95.2	49.62	327	-10.6	-9.6	-1	1
943	1976-01-02	INDIAN BAY	MAN	5031320	-95.2	49.62	327	-12.2	-11.8	-0.4	1
944	1976-01-25	INDIAN BAY	MAN	5031320	-95.2	49.62	327	-12.2	-11	-1.2	1
945	1976-02-18	INDIAN BAY	MAN	5031320	-95.2	49.62	327	-1.1	-0.7	-0.4	1
946	1976-02-27	INDIAN BAY	MAN	5031320	-95.2	49.62	327	-12.2	-10.5	-1.7	1
947	1976-09-03	INDIAN BAY	MAN	5031320	-95.2	49.62	327	15	15.1	-0.1	1
948	1976-11-19	INDIAN BAY	MAN	5031320	-95.2	49.62	327	-0.6	-0.2	-0.4	1
949	1976-11-26	INDIAN BAY	MAN	5031320	-95.2	49.62	327	-14.4	-13.1	-1.3	1
950	1976-12-19	INDIAN BAY	MAN	5031320	-95.2	49.62	327	-12.2	-10.5	-1.7	1
951	1977-01-06	INDIAN BAY	MAN	5031320	-95.2	49.62	327	-18.3	-17	-1.3	1

952	1977-01-30	INDIAN BAY	MAN	5031320	-95.2	49.62	327	-18.3	-17.6	-0.7	1
953	1977-05-05	INDIAN BAY	MAN	5031320	-95.2	49.62	327	12.2	12.8	-0.6	1
954	1977-06-28	INDIAN BAY	MAN	5031320	-95.2	49.62	327	20.6	20.9	-0.3	1
955	1977-09-24	INDIAN BAY	MAN	5031320	-95.2	49.62	327	11.7	12.2	-0.5	1
956	1977-11-09	INDIAN BAY	MAN	5031320	-95.2	49.62	327	-1.7	-1.1	-0.6	1
957	1977-11-17	INDIAN BAY	MAN	5031320	-95.2	49.62	327	-2.8	-2.2	-0.6	1
958	1977-11-21	INDIAN BAY	MAN	5031320	-95.2	49.62	327	-12.8	-11.8	-1	1
959	1977-12-19	INDIAN BAY	MAN	5031320	-95.2	49.62	327	-5.6	-4.7	-0.9	1
960	1977-12-24	INDIAN BAY	MAN	5031320	-95.2	49.62	327	-20	-19.7	-0.3	1
961	1978-05-19	INDIAN BAY	MAN	5031320	-95.2	49.62	327	11.1	12.2	-1.1	1
962	1978-08-15	INDIAN BAY	MAN	5031320	-95.2	49.62	327	16.1	17	-0.9	1
963	1978-11-18	INDIAN BAY	MAN	5031320	-95.2	49.62	327	-10.6	-10.1	-0.5	1
964	1978-11-27	INDIAN BAY	MAN	5031320	-95.2	49.62	327	-12.2	-10.5	-1.7	1
965	1978-12-05	INDIAN BAY	MAN	5031320	-95.2	49.62	327	-12.2	-10.5	-1.7	1
966	1978-12-20	INDIAN BAY	MAN	5031320	-95.2	49.62	327	-8.9	-7.9	-1	1
967	1978-12-22	INDIAN BAY	MAN	5031320	-95.2	49.62	327	-13.9	-12.7	-1.2	1
968	1979-02-23	INDIAN BAY	MAN	5031320	-95.2	49.62	327	-10	-9.3	-0.7	1
969	1979-03-09	INDIAN BAY	MAN	5031320	-95.2	49.62	327	-17.8	-16.4	-1.4	1
970	1979-10-31	INDIAN BAY	MAN	5031320	-95.2	49.62	327	1.1	1.5	-0.4	1
971	1979-11-01	INDIAN BAY	MAN	5031320	-95.2	49.62	327	-0.6	-0.2	-0.4	1
972	1979-11-07	INDIAN BAY	MAN	5031320	-95.2	49.62	327	-3.9	-3.4	-0.5	1
973	1979-12-11	INDIAN BAY	MAN	5031320	-95.2	49.62	327	-16.1	-15	-1.1	1
974	1979-12-15	INDIAN BAY	MAN	5031320	-95.2	49.62	327	-18.9	-16.4	-2.5	1
975	1979-12-22	INDIAN BAY	MAN	5031320	-95.2	49.62	327	-1.7	-1.1	-0.6	1
976	1979-12-23	INDIAN BAY	MAN	5031320	-95.2	49.62	327	-2.8	-2.2	-0.6	1
977	1980-01-07	INDIAN BAY	MAN	5031320	-95.2	49.62	327	-20.6	-18.6	-2	1
978	1980-01-22	INDIAN BAY	MAN	5031320	-95.2	49.62	327	-16.7	-15.4	-1.3	1
979	1980-12-06	INDIAN BAY	MAN	5031320	-95.2	49.62	327	-11	-10.4	-0.6	1
980	1980-12-09	INDIAN BAY	MAN	5031320	-95.2	49.62	327	-19	-18	-1	1
981	1980-12-18	INDIAN BAY	MAN	5031320	-95.2	49.62	327	-23	-21.9	-1.1	1
982	1981-01-01	INDIAN BAY	MAN	5031320	-95.2	49.62	327	-12.5	-11.1	-1.4	1
983	1981-01-06	INDIAN BAY	MAN	5031320	-95.2	49.62	327	-17	-14.7	-2.3	1
984	1981-01-14	INDIAN BAY	MAN	5031320	-95.2	49.62	327	-14	-12.2	-1.8	1
985	1981-02-09	INDIAN BAY	MAN	5031320	-95.2	49.62	327	-24	-23.5	-0.5	1

986	1981-05-24	INDIAN BAY	MAN	5031320	-95.2	49.62	327	12	12.1	-0.1	1
987	1981-12-23	INDIAN BAY	MAN	5031320	-95.2	49.62	327	-12	-11.8	-0.2	1
988	1982-01-23	INDIAN BAY	MAN	5031320	-95.2	49.62	327	-19.5	-18.9	-0.6	1
989	1982-02-22	INDIAN BAY	MAN	5031320	-95.2	49.62	327	-5	-4.6	-0.4	1
990	1982-03-31	INDIAN BAY	MAN	5031320	-95.2	49.62	327	-0.5	-0.1	-0.4	1
991	1982-09-11	INDIAN BAY	MAN	5031320	-95.2	49.62	327	20	20.5	-0.5	1
992	1982-09-27	INDIAN BAY	MAN	5031320	-95.2	49.62	327	9	9.3	-0.3	1
993	1982-12-06	INDIAN BAY	MAN	5031320	-95.2	49.62	327	-13.5	-11.4	-2.1	1
994	1982-12-10	INDIAN BAY	MAN	5031320	-95.2	49.62	327	-19	-18	-1	1
995	1982-12-28	INDIAN BAY	MAN	5031320	-95.2	49.62	327	-16	-15.1	-0.9	1
996	1983-01-24	INDIAN BAY	MAN	5031320	-95.2	49.62	327	-17	-15.1	-1.9	1
997	1983-01-29	INDIAN BAY	MAN	5031320	-95.2	49.62	327	-9	-8.3	-0.7	1
998	1983-02-02	INDIAN BAY	MAN	5031320	-95.2	49.62	327	-12	-10.7	-1.3	1
999	1983-03-07	INDIAN BAY	MAN	5031320	-95.2	49.62	327	0	0.9	-0.9	1
1000	1983-11-20	INDIAN BAY	MAN	5031320	-95.2	49.62	327	-1	-0.5	-0.5	1
1001	1983-12-08	INDIAN BAY	MAN	5031320	-95.2	49.62	327	-20	-18.4	-1.6	1
1002	1983-12-15	INDIAN BAY	MAN	5031320	-95.2	49.62	327	-19	-16.5	-2.5	1
1003	1983-12-22	INDIAN BAY	MAN	5031320	-95.2	49.62	327	-25	-24	-1	1
1004	1983-12-28	INDIAN BAY	MAN	5031320	-95.2	49.62	327	-19.5	-18.9	-0.6	1
1005	1984-01-16	INDIAN BAY	MAN	5031320	-95.2	49.62	327	-17.5	-16.5	-1	1
1006	1984-11-04	INDIAN BAY	MAN	5031320	-95.2	49.62	327	-3	-2.4	-0.6	1
1007	1984-11-15	INDIAN BAY	MAN	5031320	-95.2	49.62	327	-4	-3.5	-0.5	1
1008	1984-12-05	INDIAN BAY	MAN	5031320	-95.2	49.62	327	-18.5	-17	-1.5	1
1009	1984-12-28	INDIAN BAY	MAN	5031320	-95.2	49.62	327	-15	-13.4	-1.6	1
1010	1985-01-24	INDIAN BAY	MAN	5031320	-95.2	49.62	327	-15.5	-13.1	-2.4	1
1011	1985-11-07	INDIAN BAY	MAN	5031320	-95.2	49.62	327	-2.5	-2.4	-0.1	1
1012	1985-12-10	INDIAN BAY	MAN	5031320	-95.2	49.62	327	-13.5	-11.4	-2.1	1
1013	1985-12-12	INDIAN BAY	MAN	5031320	-95.2	49.62	327	-22	-18.9	-3.1	1
1014	1985-12-23	INDIAN BAY	MAN	5031320	-95.2	49.62	327	-16	-13.5	-2.5	1
1015	1986-01-05	INDIAN BAY	MAN	5031320	-95.2	49.62	327	-19.5	-17	-2.5	1
1016	1986-01-12	INDIAN BAY	MAN	5031320	-95.2	49.62	327	-12.5	-11.1	-1.4	1
1017	1986-01-18	INDIAN BAY	MAN	5031320	-95.2	49.62	327	-5	-4.1	-0.9	1
1018	1986-01-25	INDIAN BAY	MAN	5031320	-95.2	49.62	327	-13.5	-11.8	-1.7	1
1019	1986-02-07	INDIAN BAY	MAN	5031320	-95.2	49.62	327	-11.5	-10.4	-1.1	1

1020	1986-03-06	INDIAN BAY	MAN	5031320	-95.2	49.62	327	-17.5	-16	-1.5	1
1021	1986-04-12	INDIAN BAY	MAN	5031320	-95.2	49.62	327	-5	-4.6	-0.4	1
1022	1986-12-03	INDIAN BAY	MAN	5031320	-95.2	49.62	327	-12	-11.1	-0.9	1
1023	1986-12-09	INDIAN BAY	MAN	5031320	-95.2	49.62	327	-15.5	-15.2	-0.3	1
1024	1987-03-25	INDIAN BAY	MAN	5031320	-95.2	49.62	327	1	1.4	-0.4	1
1025	1987-11-16	INDIAN BAY	MAN	5031320	-95.2	49.62	327	0	0.4	-0.4	1
1026	1987-11-28	INDIAN BAY	MAN	5031320	-95.2	49.62	327	-2.5	-1.4	-1.1	1
1027	1987-12-09	INDIAN BAY	MAN	5031320	-95.2	49.62	327	0	0.4	-0.4	1
1028	1987-12-30	INDIAN BAY	MAN	5031320	-95.2	49.62	327	-7	-6.6	-0.4	1
1029	1988-01-30	INDIAN BAY	MAN	5031320	-95.2	49.62	327	-11	-10	-1	1
1030	1988-01-31	INDIAN BAY	MAN	5031320	-95.2	49.62	327	-20	-17.5	-2.5	1
1031	1988-02-22	INDIAN BAY	MAN	5031320	-95.2	49.62	327	-15	-13.4	-1.6	1
1032	1988-11-16	INDIAN BAY	MAN	5031320	-95.2	49.62	327	-4	-3.5	-0.5	1
1033	1988-11-25	INDIAN BAY	MAN	5031320	-95.2	49.62	327	0.5	0.8	-0.3	1
1034	1989-01-07	INDIAN BAY	MAN	5031320	-95.2	49.62	327	-11.5	-11.4	-0.1	1
1035	1989-01-08	INDIAN BAY	MAN	5031320	-95.2	49.62	327	-23.5	-20.9	-2.6	1
1036	1989-01-23	INDIAN BAY	MAN	5031320	-95.2	49.62	327	-11.5	-10.7	-0.8	1
1037	1989-01-31	INDIAN BAY	MAN	5031320	-95.2	49.62	327	-15.5	-13.4	-2.1	1
1038	1989-06-12	INDIAN BAY	MAN	5031320	-95.2	49.62	327	15	15.3	-0.3	1
1039	1990-01-11	INDIAN BAY	MAN	5031320	-95.2	49.62	327	-8.5	-8.4	-0.1	1
1040	1990-06-02	INDIAN BAY	MAN	5031320	-95.2	49.62	327	14	15.3	-1.3	1
1041	1990-12-28	INDIAN BAY	MAN	5031320	-95.2	49.62	327	-16	-13.9	-2.1	1
1042	1991-01-23	INDIAN BAY	MAN	5031320	-95.2	49.62	327	-20	-19.9	-0.1	1
1043	1991-04-30	INDIAN BAY	MAN	5031320	-95.2	49.62	327	3.5	3.8	-0.3	1
1044	1991-09-22	INDIAN BAY	MAN	5031320	-95.2	49.62	327	8.5	9.3	-0.8	1
1045	1991-12-01	INDIAN BAY	MAN	5031320	-95.2	49.62	327	-22	-20.4	-1.6	1
1046	1991-12-17	INDIAN BAY	MAN	5031320	-95.2	49.62	327	-16	-14.7	-1.3	1
1047	1992-03-07	INDIAN BAY	MAN	5031320	-95.2	49.62	327	0	0.9	-0.9	1
1048	1992-03-08	INDIAN BAY	MAN	5031320	-95.2	49.62	327	-6	-5.1	-0.9	1
1049	1992-06-18	INDIAN BAY	MAN	5031320	-95.2	49.62	327	11	11.1	-0.1	1
1050	1992-12-14	INDIAN BAY	MAN	5031320	-95.2	49.62	327	-4.5	-3.5	-1	1
1051	1992-12-19	INDIAN BAY	MAN	5031320	-95.2	49.62	327	-16	-14.3	-1.7	1
1052	1993-02-05	INDIAN BAY	MAN	5031320	-95.2	49.62	327	-9.5	-8.8	-0.7	1
1053	1993-03-16	INDIAN BAY	MAN	5031320	-95.2	49.62	327	-15.5	-14.7	-0.8	1

1054	1993-05-23	INDIAN BAY	MAN	5031320	-95.2	49.62	327	11	11.6	-0.6	1
1055	1993-11-04	INDIAN BAY	MAN	5031320	-95.2	49.62	327	-2.5	-1.9	-0.6	1
1056	1993-11-27	INDIAN BAY	MAN	5031320	-95.2	49.62	327	-7	-6.6	-0.4	1
1057	1994-01-04	INDIAN BAY	MAN	5031320	-95.2	49.62	327	-23	-21.9	-1.1	1
1058	1994-01-28	INDIAN BAY	MAN	5031320	-95.2	49.62	327	-10	-9.6	-0.4	1
1059	1994-02-19	INDIAN BAY	MAN	5031320	-95.2	49.62	327	-9	-8.4	-0.6	1
1060	1995-11-03	INDIAN BAY	MAN	5031320	-95.2	49.62	327	-9	-8.4	-0.6	1
1061	1995-12-05	INDIAN BAY	MAN	5031320	-95.2	49.62	327	-16	-15.1	-0.9	1
1062	1996-01-14	INDIAN BAY	MAN	5031320	-95.2	49.62	327	-25	-21.9	-3.1	1
1063	1996-01-18	INDIAN BAY	MAN	5031320	-95.2	49.62	327	-24.5	-24	-0.5	1
1064	1996-12-18	INDIAN BAY	MAN	5031320	-95.2	49.62	327	-16.5	-14.7	-1.8	1
1065	1997-01-22	INDIAN BAY	MAN	5031320	-95.2	49.62	327	-17	-16.1	-0.9	1
1066	1997-02-23	INDIAN BAY	MAN	5031320	-95.2	49.62	327	-12	-9.2	-2.8	1
1067	1997-04-06	INDIAN BAY	MAN	5031320	-95.2	49.62	327	-9	-7.9	-1.1	1
1068	1997-09-29	INDIAN BAY	MAN	5031320	-95.2	49.62	327	11	11.1	-0.1	1
1069	1997-12-07	INDIAN BAY	MAN	5031320	-95.2	49.62	327	-5	-4.6	-0.4	1
1070	1997-12-30	INDIAN BAY	MAN	5031320	-95.2	49.62	327	-18.5	-15.6	-2.9	1
1071	1999-11-18	INDIAN BAY	MAN	5031320	-95.2	49.62	327	-1	-0.9	-0.1	1
1072	2000-06-14	INDIAN BAY	MAN	5031320	-95.2	49.62	327	15.5	15.8	-0.3	1
1073	2001-01-15	INDIAN BAY	MAN	5031320	-95.2	49.62	327	-9	-8.7	-0.3	1
1074	2001-01-18	INDIAN BAY	MAN	5031320	-95.2	49.62	327	-14.5	-13.9	-0.6	1
1075	2001-12-28	INDIAN BAY	MAN	5031320	-95.2	49.62	327	-14	-13.8	-0.2	1
1076	2001-12-30	INDIAN BAY	MAN	5031320	-95.2	49.62	327	-14.5	-14.3	-0.2	1
1077	2002-01-27	INDIAN BAY	MAN	5031320	-95.2	49.62	327	-15.5	-14.3	-1.2	1
1078	2002-10-29	INDIAN BAY	MAN	5031320	-95.2	49.62	327	-2	-1.9	-0.1	1
1079	2013-12-27	BEATRICE	ONT	6110607	-79.4	45.13	297	-5.7	-3.3	-2.4	1
1080	1918-06-22	BROCKVILLE	ONT	6100971	-75.67	44.6	96	9.2	9.4	-0.2	1
1081	1919-03-05	BROCKVILLE	ONT	6100971	-75.67	44.6	96	3.5	3.8	-0.3	1
1082	1919-08-06	BROCKVILLE	ONT	6100971	-75.67	44.6	96	24.6	25.1	-0.5	1
1083	1920-04-06	BROCKVILLE	ONT	6100971	-75.67	44.6	96	1.3	1.8	-0.5	1
1084	1921-03-22	BROCKVILLE	ONT	6100971	-75.67	44.6	96	4.8	5.5	-0.7	1
1085	1924-11-22	BROCKVILLE	ONT	6100971	-75.67	44.6	96	7.1	7.2	-0.1	1
1086	1927-11-11	BROCKVILLE	ONT	6100971	-75.67	44.6	96	7.1	7.2	-0.1	1
1087	1927-12-11	BROCKVILLE	ONT	6100971	-75.67	44.6	96	0.8	1.2	-0.4	1

1088	1927-12-12	BROCKVILLE	ONT	6100971	-75.67	44.6	96	1.9	2.8	-0.9	1
1089	1927-12-13	BROCKVILLE	ONT	6100971	-75.67	44.6	96	0.9	1.8	-0.9	1
1090	1960-01-06	BROCKVILLE	ONT	6100971	-75.67	44.6	96	-3.1	-2.8	-0.3	1
1091	1968-12-14	BROCKVILLE	ONT	6100971	-75.67	44.6	96	1.6	1.7	-0.1	1
1092	1986-12-26	BROCKVILLE	ONT	6100971	-75.67	44.6	96	0.9	1	-0.1	1
1093	1988-12-01	BROCKVILLE	ONT	6100971	-75.67	44.6	96	0.9	1	-0.1	1
1094	2004-12-30	SYDNEY	NS	8205701	-60.05	46.17	62	-3.9	-1.3	-2.6	1
1095	1934-11-09	CARTWRIGHT	NFLD	8501100	-57.03	53.72	14	1.9	2.6	-0.7	1
1096	1934-12-03	CARTWRIGHT	NFLD	8501100	-57.03	53.72	14	-7.4	-7.3	-0.1	1
1097	1934-12-22	CARTWRIGHT	NFLD	8501100	-57.03	53.72	14	-10.9	-10	-0.9	1
1098	1935-02-25	CARTWRIGHT	NFLD	8501100	-57.03	53.72	14	-16.3	-14.7	-1.6	1
1099	1935-03-14	CARTWRIGHT	NFLD	8501100	-57.03	53.72	14	-15.1	-14.7	-0.4	1
1100	1936-01-13	CARTWRIGHT	NFLD	8501100	-57.03	53.72	14	-13	-12.1	-0.9	1
1101	1936-02-07	CARTWRIGHT	NFLD	8501100	-57.03	53.72	14	-4.8	-4.3	-0.5	1
1102	1937-12-28	CARTWRIGHT	NFLD	8501100	-57.03	53.72	14	-12.5	-12.1	-0.4	1
1103	1940-12-31	CARTWRIGHT	NFLD	8501100	-57.03	53.72	14	-9.2	-9.1	-0.1	1
1104	1941-12-23	CARTWRIGHT	NFLD	8501100	-57.03	53.72	14	-1.5	-1.2	-0.3	1
1105	1943-01-14	CARTWRIGHT	NFLD	8501100	-57.03	53.72	14	-10.9	-10.5	-0.4	1
1106	1947-06-15	CARTWRIGHT	NFLD	8501100	-57.03	53.72	14	3.5	3.8	-0.3	1
1107	1947-11-13	CARTWRIGHT	NFLD	8501100	-57.03	53.72	14	1.8	2.3	-0.5	1
1108	1947-11-18	CARTWRIGHT	NFLD	8501100	-57.03	53.72	14	1.2	1.7	-0.5	1
1109	1955-02-09	CARTWRIGHT	NFLD	8501100	-57.03	53.72	14	-16.3	-16.1	-0.2	1
1110	1958-12-01	CARTWRIGHT	NFLD	8501100	-57.03	53.72	14	-12.5	-12.1	-0.4	1
1111	1959-01-13	CARTWRIGHT	NFLD	8501100	-57.03	53.72	14	-9.2	-8.6	-0.6	1
1112	1913-12-04	CRESTON	BC	1142160	-116.52	49.1	610	-1.7	-1.6	-0.1	1
1113	1913-12-17	CRESTON	BC	1142160	-116.52	49.1	610	-6.1	-5	-1.1	1
1114	1915-11-15	CRESTON	BC	1142160	-116.52	49.1	610	0	0.7	-0.7	1
1115	1915-11-25	CRESTON	BC	1142160	-116.52	49.1	610	3.3	3.6	-0.3	1
1116	1915-12-02	CRESTON	BC	1142160	-116.52	49.1	610	-3.3	-2.2	-1.1	1
1117	1915-12-30	CRESTON	BC	1142160	-116.52	49.1	610	-12.2	-12	-0.2	1
1118	1916-01-11	CRESTON	BC	1142160	-116.52	49.1	610	-16.7	-14.6	-2.1	1
1119	1916-01-14	CRESTON	BC	1142160	-116.52	49.1	610	-11.1	-9.9	-1.2	1
1120	1916-11-25	CRESTON	BC	1142160	-116.52	49.1	610	0	1	-1	1
1121	1917-01-31	CRESTON	BC	1142160	-116.52	49.1	610	-15	-13	-2	1

1122	1917-02-13	CRESTON	BC	1142160	-116.52	49.1	610	-1.1	0.7	-1.8	1
1123	1917-02-19	CRESTON	BC	1142160	-116.52	49.1	610	-5.6	-5	-0.6	1
1124	1917-11-29	CRESTON	BC	1142160	-116.52	49.1	610	1.1	1.4	-0.3	1
1125	1917-11-30	CRESTON	BC	1142160	-116.52	49.1	610	1.1	1.4	-0.3	1
1126	1917-12-12	CRESTON	BC	1142160	-116.52	49.1	610	-5.6	-5.5	-0.1	1
1127	1917-12-25	CRESTON	BC	1142160	-116.52	49.1	610	-7.2	-6.9	-0.3	1
1128	1917-12-26	CRESTON	BC	1142160	-116.52	49.1	610	-5	-4.2	-0.8	1
1129	1917-12-30	CRESTON	BC	1142160	-116.52	49.1	610	1.7	1.9	-0.2	1
1130	1918-12-24	CRESTON	BC	1142160	-116.52	49.1	610	-2.2	-0.9	-1.3	1
1131	1918-12-25	CRESTON	BC	1142160	-116.52	49.1	610	-3.9	-3.7	-0.2	1
1132	1919-01-01	CRESTON	BC	1142160	-116.52	49.1	610	-11.7	-9.8	-1.9	1
1133	1919-12-08	CRESTON	BC	1142160	-116.52	49.1	610	-12.2	-10.8	-1.4	1
1134	1919-12-10	CRESTON	BC	1142160	-116.52	49.1	610	-15	-14.6	-0.4	1
1135	1919-12-11	CRESTON	BC	1142160	-116.52	49.1	610	-15.6	-15.2	-0.4	1
1136	1920-01-20	CRESTON	BC	1142160	-116.52	49.1	610	-8.9	-6.8	-2.1	1
1137	1920-01-26	CRESTON	BC	1142160	-116.52	49.1	610	-6.1	-6	-0.1	1
1138	1920-02-23	CRESTON	BC	1142160	-116.52	49.1	610	2.2	2.4	-0.2	1
1139	1921-01-15	CRESTON	BC	1142160	-116.52	49.1	610	2.8	3.1	-0.3	1
1140	1921-02-02	CRESTON	BC	1142160	-116.52	49.1	610	-2.8	-2.1	-0.7	1
1141	1921-03-10	CRESTON	BC	1142160	-116.52	49.1	610	-3.3	-2.5	-0.8	1
1142	1921-11-21	CRESTON	BC	1142160	-116.52	49.1	610	-12.2	-11.4	-0.8	1
1143	1921-12-17	CRESTON	BC	1142160	-116.52	49.1	610	-10.6	-7.9	-2.7	1
1144	1921-12-18	CRESTON	BC	1142160	-116.52	49.1	610	-13.9	-10.9	-3	1
1145	1923-02-12	CRESTON	BC	1142160	-116.52	49.1	610	-16.1	-15.7	-0.4	1
1146	1925-05-21	CRESTON	BC	1142160	-116.52	49.1	610	13.3	13.8	-0.5	1
1147	1925-12-09	CRESTON	BC	1142160	-116.52	49.1	610	2.8	3.1	-0.3	1
1148	1926-08-30	CRESTON	BC	1142160	-116.52	49.1	610	14.4	14.5	-0.1	1
1149	1926-12-12	CRESTON	BC	1142160	-116.52	49.1	610	-9.4	-7.3	-2.1	1
1150	1927-01-18	CRESTON	BC	1142160	-116.52	49.1	610	-5.6	-5	-0.6	1
1151	1927-01-19	CRESTON	BC	1142160	-116.52	49.1	610	-8.3	-8.1	-0.2	1
1152	1927-01-25	CRESTON	BC	1142160	-116.52	49.1	610	-5	-4.3	-0.7	1
1153	1927-01-27	CRESTON	BC	1142160	-116.52	49.1	610	-0.6	0.7	-1.3	1
1154	1927-09-13	CRESTON	BC	1142160	-116.52	49.1	610	9.4	10.2	-0.8	1
1155	1927-10-23	CRESTON	BC	1142160	-116.52	49.1	610	11.7	13.3	-1.6	1

1156	1927-12-14	CRESTON	BC	1142160	-116.52	49.1	610	-11.1	-10.4	-0.7	1
1157	1927-12-29	CRESTON	BC	1142160	-116.52	49.1	610	-6.7	-5.5	-1.2	1
1158	1928-11-28	CRESTON	BC	1142160	-116.52	49.1	610	1.1	1.5	-0.4	1
1159	1928-11-29	CRESTON	BC	1142160	-116.52	49.1	610	0	0.7	-0.7	1
1160	1928-12-15	CRESTON	BC	1142160	-116.52	49.1	610	-2.2	-1.9	-0.3	1
1161	1929-01-01	CRESTON	BC	1142160	-116.52	49.1	610	-5	-3	-2	1
1162	1929-01-12	CRESTON	BC	1142160	-116.52	49.1	610	-2.8	-2.5	-0.3	1
1163	1929-04-29	CRESTON	BC	1142160	-116.52	49.1	610	7.2	8	-0.8	1
1164	1929-12-09	CRESTON	BC	1142160	-116.52	49.1	610	-4.4	-3.7	-0.7	1
1165	1930-01-14	CRESTON	BC	1142160	-116.52	49.1	610	-11.1	-9.5	-1.6	1
1166	1930-01-15	CRESTON	BC	1142160	-116.52	49.1	610	-17.2	-14.6	-2.6	1
1167	1930-01-19	CRESTON	BC	1142160	-116.52	49.1	610	-9.4	-7.5	-1.9	1
1168	1930-10-26	CRESTON	BC	1142160	-116.52	49.1	610	4.4	5.1	-0.7	1
1169	1930-11-12	CRESTON	BC	1142160	-116.52	49.1	610	1.7	3	-1.3	1
1170	1930-11-13	CRESTON	BC	1142160	-116.52	49.1	610	-1.7	-0.8	-0.9	1
1171	1930-11-22	CRESTON	BC	1142160	-116.52	49.1	610	-1.1	-0.8	-0.3	1
1172	1930-12-08	CRESTON	BC	1142160	-116.52	49.1	610	-3.3	-3	-0.3	1
1173	1931-11-07	CRESTON	BC	1142160	-116.52	49.1	610	7.2	8	-0.8	1
1174	1932-01-13	CRESTON	BC	1142160	-116.52	49.1	610	-10.6	-9.4	-1.2	1
1175	1932-02-09	CRESTON	BC	1142160	-116.52	49.1	610	0.6	0.7	-0.1	1
1176	1932-12-05	CRESTON	BC	1142160	-116.52	49.1	610	0	0.7	-0.7	1
1177	1933-01-15	CRESTON	BC	1142160	-116.52	49.1	610	-4.4	-3.7	-0.7	1
1178	1933-12-23	CRESTON	BC	1142160	-116.52	49.1	610	-1.1	0.1	-1.2	1
1179	1934-12-26	CRESTON	BC	1142160	-116.52	49.1	610	-10.6	-8.6	-2	1
1180	1935-01-18	CRESTON	BC	1142160	-116.52	49.1	610	-15.6	-15.2	-0.4	1
1181	1936-02-12	CRESTON	BC	1142160	-116.52	49.1	610	-12.8	-12.5	-0.3	1
1182	1937-01-05	CRESTON	BC	1142160	-116.52	49.1	610	-12.2	-10.4	-1.8	1
1183	1937-01-27	CRESTON	BC	1142160	-116.52	49.1	610	-9.4	-7.9	-1.5	1
1184	1937-01-28	CRESTON	BC	1142160	-116.52	49.1	610	-10	-9.9	-0.1	1
1185	1938-12-27	CRESTON	BC	1142160	-116.52	49.1	610	-7.8	-7.4	-0.4	1
1186	1938-12-28	CRESTON	BC	1142160	-116.52	49.1	610	-7.2	-7.1	-0.1	1
1187	1939-02-07	CRESTON	BC	1142160	-116.52	49.1	610	-12.2	-10.4	-1.8	1
1188	1939-10-24	CRESTON	BC	1142160	-116.52	49.1	610	1.7	1.9	-0.2	1
1189	1941-05-17	CRESTON	BC	1142160	-116.52	49.1	610	10.6	10.7	-0.1	1

1190	1941-09-12	CRESTON	BC	1142160	-116.52	49.1	610	12.2	13.8	-1.6	1
1191	1941-09-13	CRESTON	BC	1142160	-116.52	49.1	610	7.2	8	-0.8	1
1192	1941-11-15	CRESTON	BC	1142160	-116.52	49.1	610	6.1	6.8	-0.7	1
1193	1941-11-17	CRESTON	BC	1142160	-116.52	49.1	610	4.4	4.6	-0.2	1
1194	1941-12-03	CRESTON	BC	1142160	-116.52	49.1	610	7.8	9.1	-1.3	1
1195	1941-12-12	CRESTON	BC	1142160	-116.52	49.1	610	0	1.1	-1.1	1
1196	1941-12-14	CRESTON	BC	1142160	-116.52	49.1	610	0.6	1.4	-0.8	1
1197	1941-12-30	CRESTON	BC	1142160	-116.52	49.1	610	-8.9	-7.1	-1.8	1
1198	1942-05-26	CRESTON	BC	1142160	-116.52	49.1	610	11.1	11.4	-0.3	1
1199	1942-11-28	CRESTON	BC	1142160	-116.52	49.1	610	0	0.1	-0.1	1
1200	1943-01-11	CRESTON	BC	1142160	-116.52	49.1	610	-3.9	-3	-0.9	1
1201	1943-01-16	CRESTON	BC	1142160	-116.52	49.1	610	-16.1	-14.6	-1.5	1
1202	1947-12-25	CRESTON	BC	1142160	-116.52	49.1	610	1.7	1.9	-0.2	1
1203	1990-02-07	YORKTON	SASK	4019082	-102.47	51.27	527	-12.9	-11.5	-1.4	1
1204	1996-11-29	YORKTON	SASK	4019082	-102.47	51.27	527	-9.4	-8.8	-0.6	1
1205	1965-09-01	BAIE COMEAU	QUE	704S001	-68.2	49.13	130	8.9	9.3	-0.4	1
1206	1966-11-29	BAIE COMEAU	QUE	704S001	-68.2	49.13	130	5.6	5.8	-0.2	1
1207	1967-04-19	BAIE COMEAU	QUE	704S001	-68.2	49.13	130	1.7	2.2	-0.5	1
1208	1967-05-20	BAIE COMEAU	QUE	704S001	-68.2	49.13	130	3.9	4.2	-0.3	1
1209	1967-09-30	BAIE COMEAU	QUE	704S001	-68.2	49.13	130	10	10.6	-0.6	1
1210	1967-10-10	BAIE COMEAU	QUE	704S001	-68.2	49.13	130	6.1	6.2	-0.1	1
1211	1968-10-17	BAIE COMEAU	QUE	704S001	-68.2	49.13	130	7.8	8	-0.2	1
1212	1969-09-08	BAIE COMEAU	QUE	704S001	-68.2	49.13	130	10	10.1	-0.1	1
1213	1969-09-09	BAIE COMEAU	QUE	704S001	-68.2	49.13	130	10	11.1	-1.1	1
1214	1969-09-26	BAIE COMEAU	QUE	704S001	-68.2	49.13	130	7.8	8.1	-0.3	1
1215	1969-11-10	BAIE COMEAU	QUE	704S001	-68.2	49.13	130	2.2	2.9	-0.7	1
1216	1969-11-12	BAIE COMEAU	QUE	704S001	-68.2	49.13	130	5.6	5.8	-0.2	1
1217	1970-09-04	BAIE COMEAU	QUE	704S001	-68.2	49.13	130	11.7	11.9	-0.2	1
1218	1970-09-05	BAIE COMEAU	QUE	704S001	-68.2	49.13	130	10.6	11.7	-1.1	1
1219	1970-09-21	BAIE COMEAU	QUE	704S001	-68.2	49.13	130	8.3	9.3	-1	1
1220	1970-09-22	BAIE COMEAU	QUE	704S001	-68.2	49.13	130	9.4	10	-0.6	1
1221	1972-06-01	BAIE COMEAU	QUE	704S001	-68.2	49.13	130	7.2	7.4	-0.2	1
1222	1972-06-24	BAIE COMEAU	QUE	704S001	-68.2	49.13	130	10	10.6	-0.6	1
1223	1972-11-11	BAIE COMEAU	QUE	704S001	-68.2	49.13	130	1.1	1.4	-0.3	1

1224	1972-11-12	BAIE COMEAU	QUE	704S001	-68.2	49.13	130	1.1	1.4	-0.3	1
1225	1973-05-03	BAIE COMEAU	QUE	704S001	-68.2	49.13	130	3.3	3.7	-0.4	1
1226	1973-05-04	BAIE COMEAU	QUE	704S001	-68.2	49.13	130	3.3	3.7	-0.4	1
1227	1973-05-10	BAIE COMEAU	QUE	704S001	-68.2	49.13	130	5	5.2	-0.2	1
1228	1974-04-05	BAIE COMEAU	QUE	704S001	-68.2	49.13	130	1.1	1.3	-0.2	1
1229	1974-04-15	BAIE COMEAU	QUE	704S001	-68.2	49.13	130	1.1	1.4	-0.3	1
1230	1974-04-22	BAIE COMEAU	QUE	704S001	-68.2	49.13	130	2.8	2.9	-0.1	1
1231	1974-04-29	BAIE COMEAU	QUE	704S001	-68.2	49.13	130	1.7	2.9	-1.2	1
1232	1974-05-08	BAIE COMEAU	QUE	704S001	-68.2	49.13	130	2.8	2.9	-0.1	1
1233	1974-05-24	BAIE COMEAU	QUE	704S001	-68.2	49.13	130	7.2	7.4	-0.2	1
1234	1974-10-17	BAIE COMEAU	QUE	704S001	-68.2	49.13	130	4.4	4.8	-0.4	1
1235	1977-06-12	BAIE COMEAU	QUE	704S001	-68.2	49.13	130	10.3	10.9	-0.6	1
1236	1977-09-05	BAIE COMEAU	QUE	704S001	-68.2	49.13	130	11.2	11.6	-0.4	1
1237	1977-10-15	BAIE COMEAU	QUE	704S001	-68.2	49.13	130	5.1	5.8	-0.7	1
1238	1977-10-20	BAIE COMEAU	QUE	704S001	-68.2	49.13	130	6.6	7.1	-0.5	1
1239	1978-10-06	BAIE COMEAU	QUE	704S001	-68.2	49.13	130	9.4	9.7	-0.3	1
1240	1979-01-30	BAIE COMEAU	QUE	704S001	-68.2	49.13	130	4.7	4.8	-0.1	1
1241	1979-10-04	BAIE COMEAU	QUE	704S001	-68.2	49.13	130	9.6	9.8	-0.2	1
1242	1979-11-24	BAIE COMEAU	QUE	704S001	-68.2	49.13	130	2.4	2.6	-0.2	1
1243	1980-05-06	BAIE COMEAU	QUE	704S001	-68.2	49.13	130	6.2	6.3	-0.1	1
1244	1980-05-07	BAIE COMEAU	QUE	704S001	-68.2	49.13	130	5.4	5.8	-0.4	1
1245	1980-09-21	BAIE COMEAU	QUE	704S001	-68.2	49.13	130	8.9	9	-0.1	1
1246	1980-09-22	BAIE COMEAU	QUE	704S001	-68.2	49.13	130	8.3	9	-0.7	1
1247	1981-02-22	BAIE COMEAU	QUE	704S001	-68.2	49.13	130	1.7	2.1	-0.4	1
1248	1981-10-27	BAIE COMEAU	QUE	704S001	-68.2	49.13	130	5.5	5.8	-0.3	1
1249	1982-06-20	BAIE COMEAU	QUE	704S001	-68.2	49.13	130	10.9	11.1	-0.2	1
1250	1982-10-15	BAIE COMEAU	QUE	704S001	-68.2	49.13	130	8.1	9	-0.9	1
1251	1983-05-08	BAIE COMEAU	QUE	704S001	-68.2	49.13	130	4.8	4.9	-0.1	1
1252	1983-05-31	BAIE COMEAU	QUE	704S001	-68.2	49.13	130	6.1	6.3	-0.2	1
1253	1983-11-22	BAIE COMEAU	QUE	704S001	-68.2	49.13	130	1	1.4	-0.4	1
1254	1983-11-25	BAIE COMEAU	QUE	704S001	-68.2	49.13	130	1.2	1.4	-0.2	1
1255	1985-11-07	BAIE COMEAU	QUE	704S001	-68.2	49.13	130	4.3	4.7	-0.4	1
1256	1986-10-13	BAIE COMEAU	QUE	704S001	-68.2	49.13	130	6.5	6.7	-0.2	1
1257	1988-11-03	BAIE COMEAU	QUE	704S001	-68.2	49.13	130	4.5	4.6	-0.1	1

1258	1989-06-01	BAIE COMEAU	QUE	704S001	-68.2	49.13	130	10.8	10.9	-0.1	1
1259	1990-11-23	BAIE COMEAU	QUE	704S001	-68.2	49.13	130	1.4	1.9	-0.5	1
1260	1990-11-24	BAIE COMEAU	QUE	704S001	-68.2	49.13	130	1.8	2.1	-0.3	1
1261	1991-05-01	BAIE COMEAU	QUE	704S001	-68.2	49.13	130	3.7	4.1	-0.4	1
1262	1993-04-16	BAIE COMEAU	QUE	704S001	-68.2	49.13	130	2.4	2.9	-0.5	1
1263	1993-09-18	BAIE COMEAU	QUE	704S001	-68.2	49.13	130	10.5	10.9	-0.4	1
1264	1994-10-21	BAIE COMEAU	QUE	704S001	-68.2	49.13	130	8.8	10	-1.2	1
1265	1994-12-22	BAIE COMEAU	QUE	704S001	-68.2	49.13	130	2.2	2.4	-0.2	1
1266	1995-03-16	BAIE COMEAU	QUE	704S001	-68.2	49.13	130	0.1	0.3	-0.2	1
1267	1995-04-13	BAIE COMEAU	QUE	704S001	-68.2	49.13	130	1.3	1.6	-0.3	1
1268	1995-05-18	BAIE COMEAU	QUE	704S001	-68.2	49.13	130	6.1	6.2	-0.1	1
1269	1995-10-11	BAIE COMEAU	QUE	704S001	-68.2	49.13	130	7	7.5	-0.5	1
1270	1995-10-28	BAIE COMEAU	QUE	704S001	-68.2	49.13	130	8.3	8.8	-0.5	1
1271	1995-12-22	BAIE COMEAU	QUE	704S001	-68.2	49.13	130	3.3	3.5	-0.2	1
1272	1996-10-09	BAIE COMEAU	QUE	704S001	-68.2	49.13	130	6.8	6.9	-0.1	1
1273	1996-11-19	BAIE COMEAU	QUE	704S001	-68.2	49.13	130	2.1	2.5	-0.4	1
1274	1996-11-21	BAIE COMEAU	QUE	704S001	-68.2	49.13	130	1.7	1.8	-0.1	1
1275	1996-12-18	BAIE COMEAU	QUE	704S001	-68.2	49.13	130	2	2.1	-0.1	1
1276	1998-10-14	BAIE COMEAU	QUE	704S001	-68.2	49.13	130	7.6	7.7	-0.1	1
1277	1998-10-15	BAIE COMEAU	QUE	704S001	-68.2	49.13	130	7.7	8.3	-0.6	1
1278	1998-11-23	BAIE COMEAU	QUE	704S001	-68.2	49.13	130	3	3.2	-0.2	1
1279	1999-12-10	BAIE COMEAU	QUE	704S001	-68.2	49.13	130	0.7	1.3	-0.6	1
1280	1999-12-13	BAIE COMEAU	QUE	704S001	-68.2	49.13	130	1.1	1.6	-0.5	1
1281	2000-11-04	BAIE COMEAU	QUE	704S001	-68.2	49.13	130	4.7	5.6	-0.9	1
1282	2000-11-05	BAIE COMEAU	QUE	704S001	-68.2	49.13	130	5.2	5.8	-0.6	1
1283	2000-11-10	BAIE COMEAU	QUE	704S001	-68.2	49.13	130	5.1	5.5	-0.4	1
1284	2000-11-14	BAIE COMEAU	QUE	704S001	-68.2	49.13	130	4.7	4.9	-0.2	1
1285	2001-06-03	BAIE COMEAU	QUE	704S001	-68.2	49.13	130	10.9	11.2	-0.3	1
1286	2001-10-04	BAIE COMEAU	QUE	704S001	-68.2	49.13	130	7.3	8	-0.7	1
1287	2002-09-08	BAIE COMEAU	QUE	704S001	-68.2	49.13	130	11.5	11.6	-0.1	1
1288	2002-10-10	BAIE COMEAU	QUE	704S001	-68.2	49.13	130	5.2	6	-0.8	1
1289	2002-12-22	BAIE COMEAU	QUE	704S001	-68.2	49.13	130	0.3	0.7	-0.4	1
1290	2003-04-23	BAIE COMEAU	QUE	704S001	-68.2	49.13	130	3.1	3.2	-0.1	1
1291	2004-06-23	BAIE COMEAU	QUE	704S001	-68.2	49.13	130	10.8	11.5	-0.7	1

1292	2012-12-16	BAIE COMEAU	QUE	704S001	-68.2	49.13	130	-8	-1.5	-6.5	1
1293	2012-12-24	BAIE COMEAU	QUE	704S001	-68.2	49.13	130	-11.5	-11.1	-0.4	1
1294	1984-01-20	LENOXVILLE	QUE	7024280	-71.82	45.37	181	-19.5	-17	-2.5	1
1295	1984-01-25	LENOXVILLE	QUE	7024280	-71.82	45.37	181	-8.5	-1	-7.5	1
1296	1899-01-11	MONCTON	NB	8103201	-64.68	46.1	71	-20.6	-20.1	-0.5	1
1297	1899-02-13	MONCTON	NB	8103201	-64.68	46.1	71	-16.2	-15.9	-0.3	1
1298	1902-12-05	MONCTON	NB	8103201	-64.68	46.1	71	-10.6	-10.4	-0.2	1
1299	1903-01-17	MONCTON	NB	8103201	-64.68	46.1	71	-21.8	-21.7	-0.1	1
1300	1903-10-11	MONCTON	NB	8103201	-64.68	46.1	71	9.7	10	-0.3	1
1301	1905-05-01	MONCTON	NB	8103201	-64.68	46.1	71	0.8	1.4	-0.6	1
1302	1905-10-06	MONCTON	NB	8103201	-64.68	46.1	71	11	12.3	-1.3	1
1303	1906-06-03	MONCTON	NB	8103201	-64.68	46.1	71	6.9	7.2	-0.3	1
1304	1906-11-02	MONCTON	NB	8103201	-64.68	46.1	71	6.9	7.2	-0.3	1
1305	1906-12-16	MONCTON	NB	8103201	-64.68	46.1	71	-1.7	-1.5	-0.2	1
1306	1909-12-03	MONCTON	NB	8103201	-64.68	46.1	71	2.6	2.7	-0.1	1
1307	1910-11-04	MONCTON	NB	8103201	-64.68	46.1	71	6.9	7.2	-0.3	1
1308	1910-11-27	MONCTON	NB	8103201	-64.68	46.1	71	2.6	2.7	-0.1	1
1309	1910-11-28	MONCTON	NB	8103201	-64.68	46.1	71	2.6	2.7	-0.1	1
1310	1910-11-29	MONCTON	NB	8103201	-64.68	46.1	71	3.3	3.9	-0.6	1
1311	1912-07-23	MONCTON	NB	8103201	-64.68	46.1	71	11.6	12.3	-0.7	1
1312	1913-01-13	MONCTON	NB	8103201	-64.68	46.1	71	-15.6	-14.3	-1.3	1
1313	1913-10-15	MONCTON	NB	8103201	-64.68	46.1	71	12.2	12.7	-0.5	1
1314	1913-12-03	MONCTON	NB	8103201	-64.68	46.1	71	-2.2	-1.4	-0.8	1
1315	1914-02-12	MONCTON	NB	8103201	-64.68	46.1	71	-24.5	-23.9	-0.6	1
1316	1914-03-06	MONCTON	NB	8103201	-64.68	46.1	71	1.4	2	-0.6	1
1317	1914-12-24	MONCTON	NB	8103201	-64.68	46.1	71	-24.5	-20.5	-4	1
1318	1915-11-26	MONCTON	NB	8103201	-64.68	46.1	71	2.6	2.8	-0.2	1
1319	1915-12-06	MONCTON	NB	8103201	-64.68	46.1	71	1.3	2	-0.7	1
1320	1915-12-14	MONCTON	NB	8103201	-64.68	46.1	71	-1.7	-0.7	-1	1
1321	1916-12-07	MONCTON	NB	8103201	-64.68	46.1	71	0.8	1.5	-0.7	1
1322	1917-04-28	MONCTON	NB	8103201	-64.68	46.1	71	1.4	1.5	-0.1	1
1323	1917-12-29	MONCTON	NB	8103201	-64.68	46.1	71	-21.8	-21.7	-0.1	1
1324	1918-01-02	MONCTON	NB	8103201	-64.68	46.1	71	-26.2	-24.4	-1.8	1
1325	1918-11-14	MONCTON	NB	8103201	-64.68	46.1	71	0.1	0.6	-0.5	1

1326	1918-11-18	MONCTON	NB	8103201	-64.68	46.1	71	2	2.1	-0.1	1
1327	1919-05-27	MONCTON	NB	8103201	-64.68	46.1	71	6.4	6.7	-0.3	1
1328	1920-01-24	MONCTON	NB	8103201	-64.68	46.1	71	-19.5	-18	-1.5	1
1329	1922-04-02	MONCTON	NB	8103201	-64.68	46.1	71	1.3	1.4	-0.1	1
1330	1922-11-19	MONCTON	NB	8103201	-64.68	46.1	71	0.8	1.4	-0.6	1
1331	1923-02-23	MONCTON	NB	8103201	-64.68	46.1	71	-16.8	-15.4	-1.4	1
1332	1923-04-20	MONCTON	NB	8103201	-64.68	46.1	71	-0.4	0.6	-1	1
1333	1923-04-23	MONCTON	NB	8103201	-64.68	46.1	71	-0.4	-0.1	-0.3	1
1334	1923-04-24	MONCTON	NB	8103201	-64.68	46.1	71	0.1	0.6	-0.5	1
1335	1923-12-21	MONCTON	NB	8103201	-64.68	46.1	71	-0.4	-0.1	-0.3	1
1336	1924-12-21	MONCTON	NB	8103201	-64.68	46.1	71	-20.1	-18.1	-2	1
1337	1924-12-28	MONCTON	NB	8103201	-64.68	46.1	71	-20.1	-19.5	-0.6	1
1338	1925-05-10	MONCTON	NB	8103201	-64.68	46.1	71	5.1	5.6	-0.5	1
1339	1926-10-09	MONCTON	NB	8103201	-64.68	46.1	71	9.8	10.5	-0.7	1
1340	1927-01-26	MONCTON	NB	8103201	-64.68	46.1	71	-21.2	-20	-1.2	1
1341	1927-03-03	MONCTON	NB	8103201	-64.68	46.1	71	-7.9	-7.2	-0.7	1
1342	1928-12-09	MONCTON	NB	8103201	-64.68	46.1	71	0.1	0.7	-0.6	1
1343	1929-01-08	MONCTON	NB	8103201	-64.68	46.1	71	-16.2	-15.1	-1.1	1
1344	1929-01-15	MONCTON	NB	8103201	-64.68	46.1	71	-21.2	-21.1	-0.1	1
1345	1929-03-11	MONCTON	NB	8103201	-64.68	46.1	71	-12.9	-11.9	-1	1
1346	1931-02-11	MONCTON	NB	8103201	-64.68	46.1	71	-8.4	-7.7	-0.7	1
1347	1931-03-09	MONCTON	NB	8103201	-64.68	46.1	71	-1	-0.8	-0.2	1
1348	1931-03-18	MONCTON	NB	8103201	-64.68	46.1	71	-1.6	-1.5	-0.1	1
1349	1931-12-24	MONCTON	NB	8103201	-64.68	46.1	71	3.8	4.4	-0.6	1
1350	1932-04-06	MONCTON	NB	8103201	-64.68	46.1	71	0.1	0.6	-0.5	1
1351	1933-01-08	MONCTON	NB	8103201	-64.68	46.1	71	-9.5	-8.3	-1.2	1
1352	1933-01-28	MONCTON	NB	8103201	-64.68	46.1	71	-1	-0.8	-0.2	1
1353	1933-01-30	MONCTON	NB	8103201	-64.68	46.1	71	-2.2	-2	-0.2	1
1354	1933-02-09	MONCTON	NB	8103201	-64.68	46.1	71	-9	-7.2	-1.8	1
1355	1933-02-24	MONCTON	NB	8103201	-64.68	46.1	71	1.3	1.4	-0.1	1
1356	1933-03-10	MONCTON	NB	8103201	-64.68	46.1	71	-7.3	-6.2	-1.1	1
1357	1933-05-04	MONCTON	NB	8103201	-64.68	46.1	71	5.1	5.6	-0.5	1
1358	1933-11-15	MONCTON	NB	8103201	-64.68	46.1	71	-3.9	-3.1	-0.8	1
1359	1933-11-23	MONCTON	NB	8103201	-64.68	46.1	71	-3.9	-2.7	-1.2	1

1360	1933-11-25	MONCTON	NB	8103201	-64.68	46.1	71	-6.1	-5.1	-1	1
1361	1933-11-28	MONCTON	NB	8103201	-64.68	46.1	71	-10.6	-10.4	-0.2	1
1362	1933-12-01	MONCTON	NB	8103201	-64.68	46.1	71	-4.4	-3.7	-0.7	1
1363	1933-12-07	MONCTON	NB	8103201	-64.68	46.1	71	-3.3	-2.7	-0.6	1
1364	1933-12-29	MONCTON	NB	8103201	-64.68	46.1	71	-27.3	-26.1	-1.2	1
1365	1934-01-02	MONCTON	NB	8103201	-64.68	46.1	71	-16.8	-15.4	-1.4	1
1366	1934-01-08	MONCTON	NB	8103201	-64.68	46.1	71	-2.8	-2	-0.8	1
1367	1934-01-12	MONCTON	NB	8103201	-64.68	46.1	71	-3.3	-3.1	-0.2	1
1368	1934-01-15	MONCTON	NB	8103201	-64.68	46.1	71	-9.5	-8.8	-0.7	1
1369	1934-01-18	MONCTON	NB	8103201	-64.68	46.1	71	-9	-8.8	-0.2	1
1370	1934-01-26	MONCTON	NB	8103201	-64.68	46.1	71	-9	-7.7	-1.3	1
1371	1934-02-14	MONCTON	NB	8103201	-64.68	46.1	71	-14.5	-12.3	-2.2	1
1372	1934-02-24	MONCTON	NB	8103201	-64.68	46.1	71	-15.6	-13.9	-1.7	1
1373	1934-03-11	MONCTON	NB	8103201	-64.68	46.1	71	-11.8	-11	-0.8	1
1374	1934-04-12	MONCTON	NB	8103201	-64.68	46.1	71	3.3	3.9	-0.6	1
1375	1934-05-07	MONCTON	NB	8103201	-64.68	46.1	71	2.6	3.9	-1.3	1
1376	1934-10-13	MONCTON	NB	8103201	-64.68	46.1	71	5.5	6.2	-0.7	1
1377	1934-11-07	MONCTON	NB	8103201	-64.68	46.1	71	12.2	12.3	-0.1	1
1378	1934-11-20	MONCTON	NB	8103201	-64.68	46.1	71	0.8	1.4	-0.6	1
1379	1934-11-25	MONCTON	NB	8103201	-64.68	46.1	71	-1.7	-0.8	-0.9	1
1380	1934-12-02	MONCTON	NB	8103201	-64.68	46.1	71	3.3	4.4	-1.1	1
1381	1935-02-16	MONCTON	NB	8103201	-64.68	46.1	71	-2.2	-1.5	-0.7	1
1382	1935-02-26	MONCTON	NB	8103201	-64.68	46.1	71	-9.5	-9.4	-0.1	1
1383	1935-02-27	MONCTON	NB	8103201	-64.68	46.1	71	-13.4	-12.8	-0.6	1
1384	1935-03-24	MONCTON	NB	8103201	-64.68	46.1	71	-2.2	-2	-0.2	1
1385	1935-11-12	MONCTON	NB	8103201	-64.68	46.1	71	4.5	5.1	-0.6	1
1386	1935-11-14	MONCTON	NB	8103201	-64.68	46.1	71	3.8	5.1	-1.3	1
1387	1935-11-19	MONCTON	NB	8103201	-64.68	46.1	71	0.1	0.6	-0.5	1
1388	1935-12-12	MONCTON	NB	8103201	-64.68	46.1	71	-1	-0.7	-0.3	1
1389	1937-12-09	MONCTON	NB	8103201	-64.68	46.1	71	-0.4	-0.1	-0.3	1
1390	1939-01-31	MONCTON	NB	8103201	-64.68	46.1	71	-13.4	-13.2	-0.2	1
1391	1939-12-05	MONCTON	NB	8103201	-64.68	46.1	71	-3.3	-3.1	-0.2	1
1392	2007-11-18	OLIVER	BC	1125766	-119.55	49.18	297	-6	3	-9	1
1393	2010-02-21	OLIVER	BC	1125766	-119.55	49.18	297	-5.5	-4	-1.5	1

1394	2010-11-28	OLIVER	BC	1125766	-119.55	49.18	297	-5	-4	-1	1
1395	2013-11-09	OLIVER	BC	1125766	-119.55	49.18	297	5	8	-3	1
1396	2013-12-04	OLIVER	BC	1125766	-119.55	49.18	297	-7	-5	-2	1
1397	2014-11-29	OLIVER	BC	1125766	-119.55	49.18	297	-9	0	-9	1
1398	2017-02-12	OLIVER	BC	1125766	-119.55	49.18	297	3	4.5	-1.5	1
1399	1947-06-22	CLYDE	NU	2400803	-68.52	70.48	27	3.7	4.2	-0.5	1
1400	1952-01-30	CLYDE	NU	2400803	-68.52	70.48	27	-31.8	-27.6	-4.2	1
1401	1953-08-20	CLYDE	NU	2400803	-68.52	70.48	27	3	3.1	-0.1	1
1402	1987-05-07	CLYDE	NU	2400803	-68.52	70.48	27	-6.5	12.8	-19.3	1
1403	1916-01-10	GORE BAY	ONT	6092920	-82.57	45.88	189	1.5	3.2	-1.7	1
1404	1916-01-11	GORE BAY	ONT	6092920	-82.57	45.88	189	-11.2	-11.1	-0.1	1
1405	1916-01-22	GORE BAY	ONT	6092920	-82.57	45.88	189	2	2.5	-0.5	1
1406	1916-03-27	GORE BAY	ONT	6092920	-82.57	45.88	189	0.3	1.8	-1.5	1
1407	1916-04-17	GORE BAY	ONT	6092920	-82.57	45.88	189	3.9	4.4	-0.5	1
1408	1916-05-01	GORE BAY	ONT	6092920	-82.57	45.88	189	2.4	3.2	-0.8	1
1409	1916-08-22	GORE BAY	ONT	6092920	-82.57	45.88	189	20.8	21.5	-0.7	1
1410	1916-09-13	GORE BAY	ONT	6092920	-82.57	45.88	189	12.4	15.5	-3.1	1
1411	1916-10-10	GORE BAY	ONT	6092920	-82.57	45.88	189	9.2	9.3	-0.1	1
1412	1916-10-29	GORE BAY	ONT	6092920	-82.57	45.88	189	13.1	13.3	-0.2	1
1413	1916-10-30	GORE BAY	ONT	6092920	-82.57	45.88	189	4.6	6.9	-2.3	1
1414	1916-11-12	GORE BAY	ONT	6092920	-82.57	45.88	189	-3.1	-2.4	-0.7	1
1415	1916-11-24	GORE BAY	ONT	6092920	-82.57	45.88	189	-5	-4.8	-0.2	1
1416	1916-12-09	GORE BAY	ONT	6092920	-82.57	45.88	189	-1.1	0.5	-1.6	1
1417	1916-12-11	GORE BAY	ONT	6092920	-82.57	45.88	189	-7	-6.9	-0.1	1
1418	1916-12-15	GORE BAY	ONT	6092920	-82.57	45.88	189	-11.8	-11.1	-0.7	1
1419	1917-01-05	GORE BAY	ONT	6092920	-82.57	45.88	189	-1.7	-0.1	-1.6	1
1420	1917-01-21	GORE BAY	ONT	6092920	-82.57	45.88	189	-19	-16.6	-2.4	1
1421	1917-02-01	GORE BAY	ONT	6092920	-82.57	45.88	189	-19.5	-18.8	-0.7	1
1422	1917-02-04	GORE BAY	ONT	6092920	-82.57	45.88	189	-17.9	-15.8	-2.1	1
1423	1917-12-01	GORE BAY	ONT	6092920	-82.57	45.88	189	0.3	1.1	-0.8	1
1424	1917-12-09	GORE BAY	ONT	6092920	-82.57	45.88	189	-11.2	-10.6	-0.6	1
1425	1917-12-13	GORE BAY	ONT	6092920	-82.57	45.88	189	-16.2	-14.9	-1.3	1
1426	1917-12-21	GORE BAY	ONT	6092920	-82.57	45.88	189	-7	-6.4	-0.6	1
1427	1918-01-08	GORE BAY	ONT	6092920	-82.57	45.88	189	-16.8	-15.1	-1.7	1

1428	1918-02-03	GORE BAY	ONT	6092920	-82.57	45.88	189	-7.5	-7.4	-0.1	1
1429	1918-02-12	GORE BAY	ONT	6092920	-82.57	45.88	189	-5.5	-4.2	-1.3	1
1430	1918-03-05	GORE BAY	ONT	6092920	-82.57	45.88	189	-6.1	-5.3	-0.8	1
1431	1918-04-08	GORE BAY	ONT	6092920	-82.57	45.88	189	-1.7	-0.8	-0.9	1
1432	1918-08-08	GORE BAY	ONT	6092920	-82.57	45.88	189	16.3	17.1	-0.8	1
1433	1918-10-26	GORE BAY	ONT	6092920	-82.57	45.88	189	6.3	6.9	-0.6	1
1434	1918-10-30	GORE BAY	ONT	6092920	-82.57	45.88	189	7.5	8.9	-1.4	1
1435	1918-11-18	GORE BAY	ONT	6092920	-82.57	45.88	189	8.1	8.9	-0.8	1
1436	1918-11-19	GORE BAY	ONT	6092920	-82.57	45.88	189	5.8	7	-1.2	1
1437	1918-11-21	GORE BAY	ONT	6092920	-82.57	45.88	189	1	2.5	-1.5	1
1438	1918-11-25	GORE BAY	ONT	6092920	-82.57	45.88	189	-1.1	-0.8	-0.3	1
1439	1918-12-03	GORE BAY	ONT	6092920	-82.57	45.88	189	-3.2	-3.1	-0.1	1
1440	1918-12-09	GORE BAY	ONT	6092920	-82.57	45.88	189	-0.3	0.5	-0.8	1
1441	1919-01-14	GORE BAY	ONT	6092920	-82.57	45.88	189	-1	-0.1	-0.9	1
1442	1919-01-23	GORE BAY	ONT	6092920	-82.57	45.88	189	0.3	1.2	-0.9	1
1443	1919-04-10	GORE BAY	ONT	6092920	-82.57	45.88	189	3.9	4.4	-0.5	1
1444	1919-05-01	GORE BAY	ONT	6092920	-82.57	45.88	189	7.5	7.9	-0.4	1
1445	1919-05-02	GORE BAY	ONT	6092920	-82.57	45.88	189	3	4.4	-1.4	1
1446	1919-10-04	GORE BAY	ONT	6092920	-82.57	45.88	189	12.4	12.8	-0.4	1
1447	1919-11-01	GORE BAY	ONT	6092920	-82.57	45.88	189	3.4	4.4	-1	1
1448	1919-11-18	GORE BAY	ONT	6092920	-82.57	45.88	189	2	3.7	-1.7	1
1449	1919-11-22	GORE BAY	ONT	6092920	-82.57	45.88	189	3.4	4.4	-1	1
1450	1919-12-13	GORE BAY	ONT	6092920	-82.57	45.88	189	-6.1	-5.9	-0.2	1
1451	1919-12-15	GORE BAY	ONT	6092920	-82.57	45.88	189	-15.7	-14.1	-1.6	1
1452	1919-12-21	GORE BAY	ONT	6092920	-82.57	45.88	189	-2.7	-2.5	-0.2	1
1453	1920-01-01	GORE BAY	ONT	6092920	-82.57	45.88	189	-14.5	-14.4	-0.1	1
1454	1920-01-15	GORE BAY	ONT	6092920	-82.57	45.88	189	-24.5	-23.5	-1	1
1455	1920-03-29	GORE BAY	ONT	6092920	-82.57	45.88	189	0.2	0.5	-0.3	1
1456	1920-04-21	GORE BAY	ONT	6092920	-82.57	45.88	189	4.6	6.5	-1.9	1
1457	1920-04-23	GORE BAY	ONT	6092920	-82.57	45.88	189	3.9	4.9	-1	1
1458	1920-04-27	GORE BAY	ONT	6092920	-82.57	45.88	189	5.8	5.9	-0.1	1
1459	1920-04-28	GORE BAY	ONT	6092920	-82.57	45.88	189	3	3.2	-0.2	1
1460	1920-08-21	GORE BAY	ONT	6092920	-82.57	45.88	189	16.4	17.6	-1.2	1
1461	1920-09-27	GORE BAY	ONT	6092920	-82.57	45.88	189	18.8	20.4	-1.6	1

1462	1920-11-05	GORE BAY	ONT	6092920	-82.57	45.88	189	3.3	4.9	-1.6	1
1463	1920-11-09	GORE BAY	ONT	6092920	-82.57	45.88	189	3.3	4.4	-1.1	1
1464	1920-11-14	GORE BAY	ONT	6092920	-82.57	45.88	189	-1.7	-0.8	-0.9	1
1465	1920-11-18	GORE BAY	ONT	6092920	-82.57	45.88	189	-1.1	-0.1	-1	1
1466	1920-11-24	GORE BAY	ONT	6092920	-82.57	45.88	189	0.3	0.5	-0.2	1
1467	1920-12-04	GORE BAY	ONT	6092920	-82.57	45.88	189	1	2.5	-1.5	1
1468	1920-12-05	GORE BAY	ONT	6092920	-82.57	45.88	189	-3.2	-2.4	-0.8	1
1469	1920-12-14	GORE BAY	ONT	6092920	-82.57	45.88	189	4.6	6	-1.4	1
1470	1920-12-15	GORE BAY	ONT	6092920	-82.57	45.88	189	-1.7	-1.3	-0.4	1
1471	1920-12-23	GORE BAY	ONT	6092920	-82.57	45.88	189	-7	-6.9	-0.1	1
1472	1921-01-02	GORE BAY	ONT	6092920	-82.57	45.88	189	-1.7	-1.3	-0.4	1
1473	1921-01-05	GORE BAY	ONT	6092920	-82.57	45.88	189	0.3	1.9	-1.6	1
1474	1921-01-15	GORE BAY	ONT	6092920	-82.57	45.88	189	-13.4	-12.7	-0.7	1
1475	1921-01-17	GORE BAY	ONT	6092920	-82.57	45.88	189	-19.5	-17.9	-1.6	1
1476	1921-01-23	GORE BAY	ONT	6092920	-82.57	45.88	189	-3.2	-3.1	-0.1	1
1477	1921-02-23	GORE BAY	ONT	6092920	-82.57	45.88	189	-2.2	-0.1	-2.1	1
1478	1921-03-03	GORE BAY	ONT	6092920	-82.57	45.88	189	-8	-7.4	-0.6	1
1479	1921-03-21	GORE BAY	ONT	6092920	-82.57	45.88	189	-1	-0.1	-0.9	1
1480	1921-03-31	GORE BAY	ONT	6092920	-82.57	45.88	189	1	1.2	-0.2	1
1481	1921-04-15	GORE BAY	ONT	6092920	-82.57	45.88	189	2.4	2.5	-0.1	1
1482	1921-05-14	GORE BAY	ONT	6092920	-82.57	45.88	189	3.4	3.8	-0.4	1
1483	1921-08-11	GORE BAY	ONT	6092920	-82.57	45.88	189	15.9	16	-0.1	1
1484	1921-10-20	GORE BAY	ONT	6092920	-82.57	45.88	189	3.9	5.9	-2	1
1485	1921-11-15	GORE BAY	ONT	6092920	-82.57	45.88	189	1.5	1.9	-0.4	1
1486	1921-11-19	GORE BAY	ONT	6092920	-82.57	45.88	189	-0.4	-0.1	-0.3	1
1487	1921-11-22	GORE BAY	ONT	6092920	-82.57	45.88	189	-3.6	-3.1	-0.5	1
1488	1921-12-03	GORE BAY	ONT	6092920	-82.57	45.88	189	3.4	5.5	-2.1	1
1489	1921-12-05	GORE BAY	ONT	6092920	-82.57	45.88	189	-2.7	-1.9	-0.8	1
1490	1921-12-17	GORE BAY	ONT	6092920	-82.57	45.88	189	-2.7	-2.5	-0.2	1
1491	1922-01-05	GORE BAY	ONT	6092920	-82.57	45.88	189	-10.8	-10.1	-0.7	1
1492	1922-01-11	GORE BAY	ONT	6092920	-82.57	45.88	189	-7	-5.9	-1.1	1
1493	1922-01-15	GORE BAY	ONT	6092920	-82.57	45.88	189	-9.1	-9	-0.1	1
1494	1922-01-18	GORE BAY	ONT	6092920	-82.57	45.88	189	-9.1	-9	-0.1	1
1495	1922-02-02	GORE BAY	ONT	6092920	-82.57	45.88	189	-4.6	-3.6	-1	1

1496	1922-03-07	GORE BAY	ONT	6092920	-82.57	45.88	189	-1	0.5	-1.5	1
1497	1922-03-28	GORE BAY	ONT	6092920	-82.57	45.88	189	1.5	2.5	-1	1
1498	1922-10-23	GORE BAY	ONT	6092920	-82.57	45.88	189	5.1	6	-0.9	1
1499	1922-11-08	GORE BAY	ONT	6092920	-82.57	45.88	189	5.1	6	-0.9	1
1500	1922-11-19	GORE BAY	ONT	6092920	-82.57	45.88	189	-1.7	-0.1	-1.6	1
1501	1922-11-24	GORE BAY	ONT	6092920	-82.57	45.88	189	-3.6	-3.1	-0.5	1
1502	1923-01-02	GORE BAY	ONT	6092920	-82.57	45.88	189	-9.6	-9	-0.6	1
1503	1923-01-21	GORE BAY	ONT	6092920	-82.57	45.88	189	-7.1	-6.4	-0.7	1
1504	1923-05-15	GORE BAY	ONT	6092920	-82.57	45.88	189	6.3	6.4	-0.1	1
1505	1923-10-13	GORE BAY	ONT	6092920	-82.57	45.88	189	9.7	11.1	-1.4	1
1506	1923-10-29	GORE BAY	ONT	6092920	-82.57	45.88	189	5.8	6	-0.2	1
1507	1923-10-30	GORE BAY	ONT	6092920	-82.57	45.88	189	1	1.2	-0.2	1
1508	1923-11-05	GORE BAY	ONT	6092920	-82.57	45.88	189	5.1	5.5	-0.4	1
1509	1923-11-07	GORE BAY	ONT	6092920	-82.57	45.88	189	0.3	1.2	-0.9	1
1510	1923-11-16	GORE BAY	ONT	6092920	-82.57	45.88	189	4.6	6	-1.4	1
1511	1923-11-27	GORE BAY	ONT	6092920	-82.57	45.88	189	-1.7	-1.3	-0.4	1
1512	1923-12-04	GORE BAY	ONT	6092920	-82.57	45.88	189	2.1	3.1	-1	1
1513	1923-12-13	GORE BAY	ONT	6092920	-82.57	45.88	189	-0.4	-0.1	-0.3	1
1514	1923-12-25	GORE BAY	ONT	6092920	-82.57	45.88	189	0.3	0.5	-0.2	1
1515	1924-01-11	GORE BAY	ONT	6092920	-82.57	45.88	189	-14.5	-14.1	-0.4	1
1516	1924-04-10	GORE BAY	ONT	6092920	-82.57	45.88	189	-1.7	-1.3	-0.4	1
1517	1924-09-08	GORE BAY	ONT	6092920	-82.57	45.88	189	11.9	12.2	-0.3	1
1518	1924-09-22	GORE BAY	ONT	6092920	-82.57	45.88	189	13.1	13.2	-0.1	1
1519	1924-10-19	GORE BAY	ONT	6092920	-82.57	45.88	189	10.8	11.7	-0.9	1
1520	1924-11-22	GORE BAY	ONT	6092920	-82.57	45.88	189	5.1	5.5	-0.4	1
1521	1924-12-31	GORE BAY	ONT	6092920	-82.57	45.88	189	-15.1	-14.4	-0.7	1
1522	1925-01-26	GORE BAY	ONT	6092920	-82.57	45.88	189	-17.9	-17	-0.9	1
1523	1925-02-11	GORE BAY	ONT	6092920	-82.57	45.88	189	-1.7	-0.1	-1.6	1
1524	1925-04-27	GORE BAY	ONT	6092920	-82.57	45.88	189	6.3	7	-0.7	1
1525	1925-09-06	GORE BAY	ONT	6092920	-82.57	45.88	189	14.8	15.5	-0.7	1
1526	1925-10-17	GORE BAY	ONT	6092920	-82.57	45.88	189	2.4	3.2	-0.8	1
1527	1925-11-22	GORE BAY	ONT	6092920	-82.57	45.88	189	-2.2	-1.3	-0.9	1
1528	1925-12-25	GORE BAY	ONT	6092920	-82.57	45.88	189	-12.3	-12.2	-0.1	1
1529	1926-01-06	GORE BAY	ONT	6092920	-82.57	45.88	189	-1	0.5	-1.5	1

1530	1926-01-11	GORE BAY	ONT	6092920	-82.57	45.88	189	-13.4	-12.7	-0.7	1
1531	1926-01-21	GORE BAY	ONT	6092920	-82.57	45.88	189	-13.4	-12.7	-0.7	1
1532	1926-02-07	GORE BAY	ONT	6092920	-82.57	45.88	189	-12.3	-12.2	-0.1	1
1533	1926-02-15	GORE BAY	ONT	6092920	-82.57	45.88	189	-7.1	-6.4	-0.7	1
1534	1926-03-07	GORE BAY	ONT	6092920	-82.57	45.88	189	-7.1	-6.4	-0.7	1
1535	1926-05-03	GORE BAY	ONT	6092920	-82.57	45.88	189	1	1.9	-0.9	1
1536	1926-06-02	GORE BAY	ONT	6092920	-82.57	45.88	189	8.6	9.9	-1.3	1
1537	1926-06-17	GORE BAY	ONT	6092920	-82.57	45.88	189	13.1	13.6	-0.5	1
1538	1926-11-09	GORE BAY	ONT	6092920	-82.57	45.88	189	-2.2	-0.8	-1.4	1
1539	1926-11-16	GORE BAY	ONT	6092920	-82.57	45.88	189	4.6	5.9	-1.3	1
1540	1926-12-11	GORE BAY	ONT	6092920	-82.57	45.88	189	-1	-0.8	-0.2	1
1541	1926-12-31	GORE BAY	ONT	6092920	-82.57	45.88	189	-5.5	-5.3	-0.2	1
1542	1927-01-27	GORE BAY	ONT	6092920	-82.57	45.88	189	-1.7	0.5	-2.2	1
1543	1927-01-30	GORE BAY	ONT	6092920	-82.57	45.88	189	2.4	3.1	-0.7	1
1544	1927-04-06	GORE BAY	ONT	6092920	-82.57	45.88	189	2.5	4.9	-2.4	1
1545	1927-10-12	GORE BAY	ONT	6092920	-82.57	45.88	189	13.6	13.7	-0.1	1
1546	1927-11-06	GORE BAY	ONT	6092920	-82.57	45.88	189	-1	0.5	-1.5	1
1547	1927-11-17	GORE BAY	ONT	6092920	-82.57	45.88	189	-7	-6.9	-0.1	1
1548	1927-12-29	GORE BAY	ONT	6092920	-82.57	45.88	189	2.9	3.2	-0.3	1
1549	1927-12-31	GORE BAY	ONT	6092920	-82.57	45.88	189	-6.5	-5.9	-0.6	1
1550	1928-01-01	GORE BAY	ONT	6092920	-82.57	45.88	189	-16.8	-15.4	-1.4	1
1551	1928-03-26	GORE BAY	ONT	6092920	-82.57	45.88	189	-4.6	-3.1	-1.5	1
1552	1928-05-17	GORE BAY	ONT	6092920	-82.57	45.88	189	9.1	10.4	-1.3	1
1553	1928-11-12	GORE BAY	ONT	6092920	-82.57	45.88	189	3.4	5.9	-2.5	1
1554	1928-11-19	GORE BAY	ONT	6092920	-82.57	45.88	189	-1.1	0.5	-1.6	1
1555	1928-11-22	GORE BAY	ONT	6092920	-82.57	45.88	189	-0.3	-0.1	-0.2	1
1556	1928-12-17	GORE BAY	ONT	6092920	-82.57	45.88	189	2	2.4	-0.4	1
1557	1929-11-18	GORE BAY	ONT	6092920	-82.57	45.88	189	0.2	1.9	-1.7	1
1558	1929-11-24	GORE BAY	ONT	6092920	-82.57	45.88	189	-3.7	-3.1	-0.6	1
1559	1930-01-07	GORE BAY	ONT	6092920	-82.57	45.88	189	0.3	0.5	-0.2	1
1560	1930-12-06	GORE BAY	ONT	6092920	-82.57	45.88	189	-1.7	-0.2	-1.5	1
1561	1931-01-12	GORE BAY	ONT	6092920	-82.57	45.88	189	-6	-5.9	-0.1	1
1562	1931-01-27	GORE BAY	ONT	6092920	-82.57	45.88	189	-6.5	-6.4	-0.1	1
1563	1931-12-12	GORE BAY	ONT	6092920	-82.57	45.88	189	2.5	3.2	-0.7	1

1564	1931-12-24	GORE BAY	ONT	6092920	-82.57	45.88	189	2	3.2	-1.2	1
1565	1932-01-14	GORE BAY	ONT	6092920	-82.57	45.88	189	2.9	3.2	-0.3	1
1566	1932-10-26	GORE BAY	ONT	6092920	-82.57	45.88	189	8.1	8.3	-0.2	1
1567	1933-02-07	GORE BAY	ONT	6092920	-82.57	45.88	189	-20.7	-17.4	-3.3	1
1568	1933-03-03	GORE BAY	ONT	6092920	-82.57	45.88	189	0.3	1.1	-0.8	1
1569	1933-11-08	GORE BAY	ONT	6092920	-82.57	45.88	189	0.2	1.1	-0.9	1
1570	1934-01-11	GORE BAY	ONT	6092920	-82.57	45.88	189	-1	1.1	-2.1	1
1571	1934-01-25	GORE BAY	ONT	6092920	-82.57	45.88	189	-7.1	-6.9	-0.2	1
1572	1934-03-07	GORE BAY	ONT	6092920	-82.57	45.88	189	-3.6	-3.1	-0.5	1
1573	1934-04-24	GORE BAY	ONT	6092920	-82.57	45.88	189	-0.3	0.5	-0.8	1
1574	1934-10-24	GORE BAY	ONT	6092920	-82.57	45.88	189	9.1	9.9	-0.8	1
1575	1934-10-30	GORE BAY	ONT	6092920	-82.57	45.88	189	-0.3	-0.1	-0.2	1
1576	1934-12-19	GORE BAY	ONT	6092920	-82.57	45.88	189	-1.7	-1.3	-0.4	1
1577	1934-12-26	GORE BAY	ONT	6092920	-82.57	45.88	189	-7.1	-6.9	-0.2	1
1578	1935-02-03	GORE BAY	ONT	6092920	-82.57	45.88	189	-4.6	-3.6	-1	1
1579	1935-03-11	GORE BAY	ONT	6092920	-82.57	45.88	189	-0.3	-0.1	-0.2	1
1580	1935-09-29	GORE BAY	ONT	6092920	-82.57	45.88	189	9.2	10.4	-1.2	1
1581	1935-10-10	GORE BAY	ONT	6092920	-82.57	45.88	189	3.3	5.5	-2.2	1
1582	1935-10-14	GORE BAY	ONT	6092920	-82.57	45.88	189	9.2	11.1	-1.9	1
1583	1935-11-01	GORE BAY	ONT	6092920	-82.57	45.88	189	6.4	7	-0.6	1
1584	1935-11-15	GORE BAY	ONT	6092920	-82.57	45.88	189	-1.7	-1.3	-0.4	1
1585	1935-11-21	GORE BAY	ONT	6092920	-82.57	45.88	189	-1.1	-0.1	-1	1
1586	1935-11-26	GORE BAY	ONT	6092920	-82.57	45.88	189	3	3.1	-0.1	1
1587	1935-11-28	GORE BAY	ONT	6092920	-82.57	45.88	189	3.3	4.9	-1.6	1
1588	1935-12-03	GORE BAY	ONT	6092920	-82.57	45.88	189	-9.6	-9	-0.6	1
1589	1935-12-08	GORE BAY	ONT	6092920	-82.57	45.88	189	2.4	2.5	-0.1	1
1590	1935-12-10	GORE BAY	ONT	6092920	-82.57	45.88	189	1	1.2	-0.2	1
1591	1935-12-15	GORE BAY	ONT	6092920	-82.57	45.88	189	-4.1	-3.1	-1	1
1592	1935-12-19	GORE BAY	ONT	6092920	-82.57	45.88	189	-5.5	-4.8	-0.7	1
1593	1935-12-20	GORE BAY	ONT	6092920	-82.57	45.88	189	-16.8	-15.7	-1.1	1
1594	1936-01-02	GORE BAY	ONT	6092920	-82.57	45.88	189	1	1.2	-0.2	1
1595	1936-01-05	GORE BAY	ONT	6092920	-82.57	45.88	189	-0.3	-0.1	-0.2	1
1596	1936-01-06	GORE BAY	ONT	6092920	-82.57	45.88	189	-2.7	-0.8	-1.9	1
1597	1936-02-09	GORE BAY	ONT	6092920	-82.57	45.88	189	-15.7	-14.8	-0.9	1

1598	1936-02-27	GORE BAY	ONT	6092920	-82.57	45.88	189	-7.1	-6.4	-0.7	1
1599	1936-03-06	GORE BAY	ONT	6092920	-82.57	45.88	189	-6.5	-6.4	-0.1	1
1600	1936-05-02	GORE BAY	ONT	6092920	-82.57	45.88	189	3.4	4.9	-1.5	1
1601	1936-05-19	GORE BAY	ONT	6092920	-82.57	45.88	189	6.4	7.4	-1	1
1602	1936-10-10	GORE BAY	ONT	6092920	-82.57	45.88	189	10.8	11.1	-0.3	1
1603	1936-10-17	GORE BAY	ONT	6092920	-82.57	45.88	189	7	8.3	-1.3	1
1604	1936-10-21	GORE BAY	ONT	6092920	-82.57	45.88	189	3.4	5.5	-2.1	1
1605	1936-11-01	GORE BAY	ONT	6092920	-82.57	45.88	189	2.5	4.4	-1.9	1
1606	1936-11-21	GORE BAY	ONT	6092920	-82.57	45.88	189	-3.1	-1.9	-1.2	1
1607	1936-11-22	GORE BAY	ONT	6092920	-82.57	45.88	189	-7.1	-6.9	-0.2	1
1608	1936-12-31	GORE BAY	ONT	6092920	-82.57	45.88	189	-0.3	-0.1	-0.2	1
1609	1937-01-05	GORE BAY	ONT	6092920	-82.57	45.88	189	-9.6	-8.4	-1.2	1
1610	1937-01-15	GORE BAY	ONT	6092920	-82.57	45.88	189	-12.3	-11.1	-1.2	1
1611	1937-01-22	GORE BAY	ONT	6092920	-82.57	45.88	189	-8.5	-8.4	-0.1	1
1612	1937-02-14	GORE BAY	ONT	6092920	-82.57	45.88	189	-2.2	-0.8	-1.4	1
1613	1937-02-22	GORE BAY	ONT	6092920	-82.57	45.88	189	-5.5	-5.3	-0.2	1
1614	1937-11-02	GORE BAY	ONT	6092920	-82.57	45.88	189	4.5	6	-1.5	1
1615	1937-11-15	GORE BAY	ONT	6092920	-82.57	45.88	189	4.6	4.9	-0.3	1
1616	1937-11-16	GORE BAY	ONT	6092920	-82.57	45.88	189	2.5	3.2	-0.7	1
1617	1937-11-17	GORE BAY	ONT	6092920	-82.57	45.88	189	-1	-0.1	-0.9	1
1618	1937-11-18	GORE BAY	ONT	6092920	-82.57	45.88	189	-2.2	-1.9	-0.3	1
1619	1937-12-19	GORE BAY	ONT	6092920	-82.57	45.88	189	-6.1	-5.9	-0.2	1
1620	1937-12-30	GORE BAY	ONT	6092920	-82.57	45.88	189	-8.5	-8.4	-0.1	1
1621	1937-12-31	GORE BAY	ONT	6092920	-82.57	45.88	189	-16.2	-16	-0.2	1
1622	1938-01-25	GORE BAY	ONT	6092920	-82.57	45.88	189	-2.7	-1.9	-0.8	1
1623	1938-02-06	GORE BAY	ONT	6092920	-82.57	45.88	189	1	1.2	-0.2	1
1624	1938-02-09	GORE BAY	ONT	6092920	-82.57	45.88	189	-0.4	1.8	-2.2	1
1625	1938-02-13	GORE BAY	ONT	6092920	-82.57	45.88	189	-5.5	-4.8	-0.7	1
1626	1938-02-14	GORE BAY	ONT	6092920	-82.57	45.88	189	-12.3	-11.7	-0.6	1
1627	1938-02-27	GORE BAY	ONT	6092920	-82.57	45.88	189	-5.5	-4.8	-0.7	1
1628	1938-03-02	GORE BAY	ONT	6092920	-82.57	45.88	189	-7.5	-6.4	-1.1	1
1629	1938-03-23	GORE BAY	ONT	6092920	-82.57	45.88	189	2.9	3.7	-0.8	1
1630	1938-11-08	GORE BAY	ONT	6092920	-82.57	45.88	189	5.8	5.9	-0.1	1
1631	1938-11-15	GORE BAY	ONT	6092920	-82.57	45.88	189	-2.2	-1.9	-0.3	1

1632	1938-12-05	GORE BAY	ONT	6092920	-82.57	45.88	189	4.6	5.5	-0.9	1
1633	1938-12-06	GORE BAY	ONT	6092920	-82.57	45.88	189	1	1.2	-0.2	1
1634	1938-12-07	GORE BAY	ONT	6092920	-82.57	45.88	189	-0.3	-0.1	-0.2	1
1635	1938-12-17	GORE BAY	ONT	6092920	-82.57	45.88	189	-1	-0.1	-0.9	1
1636	1938-12-21	GORE BAY	ONT	6092920	-82.57	45.88	189	-5	-3.6	-1.4	1
1637	1938-12-27	GORE BAY	ONT	6092920	-82.57	45.88	189	-5	-4.8	-0.2	1
1638	1939-01-02	GORE BAY	ONT	6092920	-82.57	45.88	189	-13.4	-12.1	-1.3	1
1639	1939-01-10	GORE BAY	ONT	6092920	-82.57	45.88	189	1.5	1.9	-0.4	1
1640	1939-02-13	GORE BAY	ONT	6092920	-82.57	45.88	189	-16.2	-15.5	-0.7	1
1641	1939-10-22	GORE BAY	ONT	6092920	-82.57	45.88	189	6.3	7	-0.7	1
1642	1939-11-02	GORE BAY	ONT	6092920	-82.57	45.88	189	-0.3	-0.1	-0.2	1
1643	1939-11-08	GORE BAY	ONT	6092920	-82.57	45.88	189	3.4	4.9	-1.5	1
1644	1939-11-28	GORE BAY	ONT	6092920	-82.57	45.88	189	2.9	3.2	-0.3	1
1645	1939-12-02	GORE BAY	ONT	6092920	-82.57	45.88	189	5.1	5.5	-0.4	1
1646	1939-12-03	GORE BAY	ONT	6092920	-82.57	45.88	189	-2.2	-0.8	-1.4	1
1647	1939-12-13	GORE BAY	ONT	6092920	-82.57	45.88	189	0.3	1.1	-0.8	1
1648	1939-12-18	GORE BAY	ONT	6092920	-82.57	45.88	189	-1	-0.1	-0.9	1
1649	1939-12-30	GORE BAY	ONT	6092920	-82.57	45.88	189	-3.2	-3.1	-0.1	1
1650	1940-08-18	GORE BAY	ONT	6092920	-82.57	45.88	189	17.3	18.1	-0.8	1
1651	1940-10-14	GORE BAY	ONT	6092920	-82.57	45.88	189	8.1	8.9	-0.8	1
1652	1940-10-15	GORE BAY	ONT	6092920	-82.57	45.88	189	5.1	5.5	-0.4	1
1653	1940-11-06	GORE BAY	ONT	6092920	-82.57	45.88	189	-1.7	-1.3	-0.4	1
1654	1940-11-12	GORE BAY	ONT	6092920	-82.57	45.88	189	-4.6	-3.1	-1.5	1
1655	1940-11-14	GORE BAY	ONT	6092920	-82.57	45.88	189	-7	-6.9	-0.1	1
1656	1941-10-31	GORE BAY	ONT	6092920	-82.57	45.88	189	4.5	5.5	-1	1
1657	1941-11-02	GORE BAY	ONT	6092920	-82.57	45.88	189	3.9	4.9	-1	1
1658	1941-11-07	GORE BAY	ONT	6092920	-82.57	45.88	189	-0.3	-0.1	-0.2	1
1659	1941-11-09	GORE BAY	ONT	6092920	-82.57	45.88	189	-2.2	-0.1	-2.1	1
1660	1941-11-26	GORE BAY	ONT	6092920	-82.57	45.88	189	2	2.5	-0.5	1
1661	1942-01-09	GORE BAY	ONT	6092920	-82.57	45.88	189	-17.9	-16.1	-1.8	1
1662	1942-02-07	GORE BAY	ONT	6092920	-82.57	45.88	189	-6.5	-5.9	-0.6	1
1663	1942-03-02	GORE BAY	ONT	6092920	-82.57	45.88	189	-2.2	-0.1	-2.1	1
1664	1942-03-28	GORE BAY	ONT	6092920	-82.57	45.88	189	2.4	3.2	-0.8	1
1665	1942-09-03	GORE BAY	ONT	6092920	-82.57	45.88	189	16.9	17.6	-0.7	1

1666	1942-09-09	GORE BAY	ONT	6092920	-82.57	45.88	189	15.9	16	-0.1	1
1667	1942-10-05	GORE BAY	ONT	6092920	-82.57	45.88	189	9.2	9.9	-0.7	1
1668	1942-10-31	GORE BAY	ONT	6092920	-82.57	45.88	189	7.5	8.3	-0.8	1
1669	1942-12-02	GORE BAY	ONT	6092920	-82.57	45.88	189	-2.7	-0.8	-1.9	1
1670	1942-12-15	GORE BAY	ONT	6092920	-82.57	45.88	189	-7.1	-5.9	-1.2	1
1671	1942-12-30	GORE BAY	ONT	6092920	-82.57	45.88	189	-7	-6.4	-0.6	1
1672	1943-01-20	GORE BAY	ONT	6092920	-82.57	45.88	189	-19	-18.8	-0.2	1
1673	1943-02-01	GORE BAY	ONT	6092920	-82.57	45.88	189	-5	-4.8	-0.2	1
1674	1943-02-07	GORE BAY	ONT	6092920	-82.57	45.88	189	-5	-4.8	-0.2	1
1675	1943-10-14	GORE BAY	ONT	6092920	-82.57	45.88	189	8.1	8.4	-0.3	1
1676	1943-12-01	GORE BAY	ONT	6092920	-82.57	45.88	189	-1.7	-0.1	-1.6	1
1677	1943-12-02	GORE BAY	ONT	6092920	-82.57	45.88	189	-0.3	1.2	-1.5	1
1678	1943-12-22	GORE BAY	ONT	6092920	-82.57	45.88	189	-14	-13.6	-0.4	1
1679	1944-01-06	GORE BAY	ONT	6092920	-82.57	45.88	189	-6.5	-5.9	-0.6	1
1680	1944-04-24	GORE BAY	ONT	6092920	-82.57	45.88	189	5.8	6	-0.2	1
1681	1944-04-26	GORE BAY	ONT	6092920	-82.57	45.88	189	1.5	3.2	-1.7	1
1682	1944-11-04	GORE BAY	ONT	6092920	-82.57	45.88	189	3.3	5.9	-2.6	1
1683	1944-11-10	GORE BAY	ONT	6092920	-82.57	45.88	189	4.6	5.9	-1.3	1
1684	1944-11-15	GORE BAY	ONT	6092920	-82.57	45.88	189	3.3	5.5	-2.2	1
1685	1944-11-30	GORE BAY	ONT	6092920	-82.57	45.88	189	-6.5	-5.9	-0.6	1
1686	1944-12-28	GORE BAY	ONT	6092920	-82.57	45.88	189	-10.2	-10.1	-0.1	1
1687	1944-12-31	GORE BAY	ONT	6092920	-82.57	45.88	189	-2.2	-1.3	-0.9	1
1688	1945-02-16	GORE BAY	ONT	6092920	-82.57	45.88	189	-5	-4.8	-0.2	1
1689	1945-02-26	GORE BAY	ONT	6092920	-82.57	45.88	189	-0.3	-0.1	-0.2	1
1690	1945-08-14	GORE BAY	ONT	6092920	-82.57	45.88	189	21.8	22	-0.2	1
1691	1945-09-20	GORE BAY	ONT	6092920	-82.57	45.88	189	11.3	11.7	-0.4	1
1692	1945-09-28	GORE BAY	ONT	6092920	-82.57	45.88	189	10.2	11.7	-1.5	1
1693	1945-10-02	GORE BAY	ONT	6092920	-82.57	45.88	189	7	7.9	-0.9	1
1694	1945-10-12	GORE BAY	ONT	6092920	-82.57	45.88	189	6.3	7	-0.7	1
1695	1945-11-09	GORE BAY	ONT	6092920	-82.57	45.88	189	2	3.2	-1.2	1
1696	1945-11-19	GORE BAY	ONT	6092920	-82.57	45.88	189	-3.2	-3.1	-0.1	1
1697	1945-11-29	GORE BAY	ONT	6092920	-82.57	45.88	189	-4.6	-4.2	-0.4	1
1698	1945-12-09	GORE BAY	ONT	6092920	-82.57	45.88	189	-2.2	-0.1	-2.1	1
1699	1945-12-26	GORE BAY	ONT	6092920	-82.57	45.88	189	-4.6	-4.2	-0.4	1

1700	1945-12-29	GORE BAY	ONT	6092920	-82.57	45.88	189	-2.2	-1.3	-0.9	1
1701	1945-12-30	GORE BAY	ONT	6092920	-82.57	45.88	189	-6	-5.3	-0.7	1
1702	1946-01-07	GORE BAY	ONT	6092920	-82.57	45.88	189	1	1.9	-0.9	1
1703	1946-01-08	GORE BAY	ONT	6092920	-82.57	45.88	189	-1.7	-0.8	-0.9	1
1704	1946-01-09	GORE BAY	ONT	6092920	-82.57	45.88	189	-1.7	-1.3	-0.4	1
1705	1946-01-19	GORE BAY	ONT	6092920	-82.57	45.88	189	-19.5	-18.8	-0.7	1
1706	1946-06-24	GORE BAY	ONT	6092920	-82.57	45.88	189	24.5	25.4	-0.9	1
1707	1946-08-28	GORE BAY	ONT	6092920	-82.57	45.88	189	12.4	13.7	-1.3	1
1708	1946-11-10	GORE BAY	ONT	6092920	-82.57	45.88	189	2.5	4.9	-2.4	1
1709	1946-12-18	GORE BAY	ONT	6092920	-82.57	45.88	189	-7.1	-6.9	-0.2	1
1710	1946-12-24	GORE BAY	ONT	6092920	-82.57	45.88	189	-6.1	-5.9	-0.2	1
1711	1946-12-29	GORE BAY	ONT	6092920	-82.57	45.88	189	-16.8	-15.7	-1.1	1
1712	1947-01-20	GORE BAY	ONT	6092920	-82.57	45.88	189	-1	1.2	-2.2	1
1713	1947-03-14	GORE BAY	ONT	6092920	-82.57	45.88	189	1	1.2	-0.2	1
1714	1947-04-06	GORE BAY	ONT	6092920	-82.57	45.88	189	2.1	3.2	-1.1	1
1715	1997-09-19	GORE BAY	ONT	6092920	-82.57	45.88	189	13.5	15.1	-1.6	1
1716	1893-04-23	AGASSIZ	BC	1100120	-121.77	49.25	15	8.8	10.6	-1.8	1
1717	1893-06-07	AGASSIZ	BC	1100120	-121.77	49.25	15	11.7	12.7	-1	1
1718	1893-09-29	AGASSIZ	BC	1100120	-121.77	49.25	15	9.9	10.3	-0.4	1
1719	1893-10-21	AGASSIZ	BC	1100120	-121.77	49.25	15	11	11.1	-0.1	1
1720	1893-10-27	AGASSIZ	BC	1100120	-121.77	49.25	15	11.6	12.2	-0.6	1
1721	1893-12-09	AGASSIZ	BC	1100120	-121.77	49.25	15	6.6	8.3	-1.7	1
1722	1894-04-11	AGASSIZ	BC	1100120	-121.77	49.25	15	8.8	9.2	-0.4	1
1723	1894-05-14	AGASSIZ	BC	1100120	-121.77	49.25	15	7.8	8.3	-0.5	1
1724	1894-05-15	AGASSIZ	BC	1100120	-121.77	49.25	15	6.5	8.3	-1.8	1
1725	1894-06-26	AGASSIZ	BC	1100120	-121.77	49.25	15	12.5	13.3	-0.8	1
1726	1894-11-07	AGASSIZ	BC	1100120	-121.77	49.25	15	9.4	10.3	-0.9	1
1727	1895-02-24	AGASSIZ	BC	1100120	-121.77	49.25	15	9.4	9.6	-0.2	1
1728	1895-03-19	AGASSIZ	BC	1100120	-121.77	49.25	15	8.4	8.7	-0.3	1
1729	1895-04-13	AGASSIZ	BC	1100120	-121.77	49.25	15	9.4	9.6	-0.2	1
1730	1895-05-06	AGASSIZ	BC	1100120	-121.77	49.25	15	8.8	9.1	-0.3	1
1731	1895-05-22	AGASSIZ	BC	1100120	-121.77	49.25	15	8.8	9.1	-0.3	1
1732	1895-05-29	AGASSIZ	BC	1100120	-121.77	49.25	15	9.9	11	-1.1	1
1733	1895-09-03	AGASSIZ	BC	1100120	-121.77	49.25	15	10.4	11.1	-0.7	1

1734	1895-09-12	AGASSIZ	BC	1100120	-121.77	49.25	15	11.8	12.2	-0.4	1
1735	1895-09-22	AGASSIZ	BC	1100120	-121.77	49.25	15	8.8	9.1	-0.3	1
1736	1895-10-25	AGASSIZ	BC	1100120	-121.77	49.25	15	9.3	9.6	-0.3	1
1737	1895-11-17	AGASSIZ	BC	1100120	-121.77	49.25	15	11.1	11.6	-0.5	1
1738	1895-11-20	AGASSIZ	BC	1100120	-121.77	49.25	15	8.3	10.3	-2	1
1739	1896-02-13	AGASSIZ	BC	1100120	-121.77	49.25	15	6.8	8.6	-1.8	1
1740	1896-02-26	AGASSIZ	BC	1100120	-121.77	49.25	15	8.8	9.2	-0.4	1
1741	1896-02-27	AGASSIZ	BC	1100120	-121.77	49.25	15	6.9	8.7	-1.8	1
1742	1896-03-08	AGASSIZ	BC	1100120	-121.77	49.25	15	7.3	8.3	-1	1
1743	1896-03-24	AGASSIZ	BC	1100120	-121.77	49.25	15	10.4	11.2	-0.8	1
1744	1896-04-13	AGASSIZ	BC	1100120	-121.77	49.25	15	7.3	9.2	-1.9	1
1745	1896-04-22	AGASSIZ	BC	1100120	-121.77	49.25	15	6.8	8.7	-1.9	1
1746	1896-04-27	AGASSIZ	BC	1100120	-121.77	49.25	15	8.4	8.7	-0.3	1
1747	1898-02-14	AGASSIZ	BC	1100120	-121.77	49.25	15	5.8	6.2	-0.4	1
1748	1898-03-19	AGASSIZ	BC	1100120	-121.77	49.25	15	5.8	6.3	-0.5	1
1749	1899-03-04	AGASSIZ	BC	1100120	-121.77	49.25	15	6.3	7.2	-0.9	1
1750	1900-02-02	AGASSIZ	BC	1100120	-121.77	49.25	15	7.4	10.3	-2.9	1
1751	1900-12-12	AGASSIZ	BC	1100120	-121.77	49.25	15	7.4	7.6	-0.2	1
1752	1901-12-22	AGASSIZ	BC	1100120	-121.77	49.25	15	5.7	5.8	-0.1	1
1753	1901-12-23	AGASSIZ	BC	1100120	-121.77	49.25	15	6.3	8.3	-2	1
1754	1906-12-23	AGASSIZ	BC	1100120	-121.77	49.25	15	6.1	6.2	-0.1	1
1755	1908-02-11	AGASSIZ	BC	1100120	-121.77	49.25	15	5	5.6	-0.6	1
1756	1908-02-12	AGASSIZ	BC	1100120	-121.77	49.25	15	4.6	4.8	-0.2	1
1757	1908-02-14	AGASSIZ	BC	1100120	-121.77	49.25	15	4.7	4.8	-0.1	1
1758	1909-01-08	AGASSIZ	BC	1100120	-121.77	49.25	15	-20.2	-19.9	-0.3	1
1759	1914-01-05	AGASSIZ	BC	1100120	-121.77	49.25	15	7	7.4	-0.4	1
1760	1914-01-07	AGASSIZ	BC	1100120	-121.77	49.25	15	6.1	6.6	-0.5	1
1761	1914-01-08	AGASSIZ	BC	1100120	-121.77	49.25	15	5.6	6.2	-0.6	1
1762	1917-01-02	AGASSIZ	BC	1100120	-121.77	49.25	15	1.4	1.9	-0.5	1
1763	1917-12-29	AGASSIZ	BC	1100120	-121.77	49.25	15	3.7	3.8	-0.1	1
1764	1918-01-01	AGASSIZ	BC	1100120	-121.77	49.25	15	4.2	5.6	-1.4	1
1765	1918-02-14	AGASSIZ	BC	1100120	-121.77	49.25	15	3.9	5.7	-1.8	1
1766	1921-03-16	AGASSIZ	BC	1100120	-121.77	49.25	15	7.6	8.6	-1	1
1767	1921-12-18	AGASSIZ	BC	1100120	-121.77	49.25	15	-6.3	-6.1	-0.2	1

1768	1922-11-10	AGASSIZ	BC	1100120	-121.77	49.25	15	11	11.2	-0.2	1
1769	1923-10-16	AGASSIZ	BC	1100120	-121.77	49.25	15	6.9	7.4	-0.5	1
1770	1923-11-19	AGASSIZ	BC	1100120	-121.77	49.25	15	7.6	8.6	-1	1
1771	1923-11-26	AGASSIZ	BC	1100120	-121.77	49.25	15	5.6	6.6	-1	1
1772	1923-12-07	AGASSIZ	BC	1100120	-121.77	49.25	15	5.6	6.2	-0.6	1
1773	1923-12-15	AGASSIZ	BC	1100120	-121.77	49.25	15	5.6	6.6	-1	1
1774	2008-12-13	AGASSIZ	BC	1100120	-121.77	49.25	15	0.5	1	-0.5	1
1775	2009-02-25	AGASSIZ	BC	1100120	-121.77	49.25	15	-4	-1	-3	1
1776	2011-02-20	AGASSIZ	BC	1100120	-121.77	49.25	15	5.5	6.5	-1	1
1777	2011-02-28	AGASSIZ	BC	1100120	-121.77	49.25	15	-3.5	-2.5	-1	1
1778	2017-02-27	AGASSIZ	BC	1100120	-121.77	49.25	15	-2	-1	-1	1
1779	2017-10-24	AGASSIZ	BC	1100120	-121.77	49.25	15	7	7.5	-0.5	1
1780	2010-11-07	ESTEVAN POINT	BC	1032730	-126.55	49.38	6	6.5	7	-0.5	1
1781	1914-12-24	PRINCE GEORGE	BC	1096439	-122.68	53.88	691	-7.8	-7.5	-0.3	1
1782	1916-03-30	PRINCE GEORGE	BC	1096439	-122.68	53.88	691	4.1	4.4	-0.3	1
1783	1917-12-14	PRINCE GEORGE	BC	1096439	-122.68	53.88	691	-17.2	-17	-0.2	1
1784	1919-10-26	PRINCE GEORGE	BC	1096439	-122.68	53.88	691	-5.9	-5.2	-0.7	1
1785	1919-11-28	PRINCE GEORGE	BC	1096439	-122.68	53.88	691	-13.7	-13.5	-0.2	1
1786	1920-12-22	PRINCE GEORGE	BC	1096439	-122.68	53.88	691	-16	-15.9	-0.1	1
1787	1921-01-26	PRINCE GEORGE	BC	1096439	-122.68	53.88	691	-6.6	-6.4	-0.2	1
1788	1922-02-02	PRINCE GEORGE	BC	1096439	-122.68	53.88	691	-5.9	-5.7	-0.2	1
1789	1922-12-16	PRINCE GEORGE	BC	1096439	-122.68	53.88	691	-17.2	-16.5	-0.7	1
1790	1922-12-17	PRINCE GEORGE	BC	1096439	-122.68	53.88	691	-2.1	-1.8	-0.3	1
1791	1923-01-19	PRINCE GEORGE	BC	1096439	-122.68	53.88	691	-19.4	-18.2	-1.2	1
1792	1923-02-15	PRINCE GEORGE	BC	1096439	-122.68	53.88	691	-10.7	-10.5	-0.2	1
1793	1923-12-13	PRINCE GEORGE	BC	1096439	-122.68	53.88	691	-4.6	-4.4	-0.2	1
1794	1924-01-04	PRINCE GEORGE	BC	1096439	-122.68	53.88	691	-9	-8.6	-0.4	1
1795	1924-01-19	PRINCE GEORGE	BC	1096439	-122.68	53.88	691	-4.6	-4.4	-0.2	1
1796	1924-02-28	PRINCE GEORGE	BC	1096439	-122.68	53.88	691	-3.9	-3.1	-0.8	1
1797	1928-11-27	PRINCE GEORGE	BC	1096439	-122.68	53.88	691	-2.7	-2.5	-0.2	1
1798	1931-11-14	PRINCE GEORGE	BC	1096439	-122.68	53.88	691	-12.5	-12.3	-0.2	1
1799	1920-11-19	HARROW	ONT	6130257	-82.9	42.03	182	0.5	0.6	-0.1	1
1800	1923-02-26	HARROW	ONT	6130257	-82.9	42.03	182	3.2	3.3	-0.1	1
1801	1934-01-01	HARROW	ONT	6130257	-82.9	42.03	182	3.2	3.3	-0.1	1

1802	1939-03-30	HARROW	ONT	6130257	-82.9	42.03	182	-1.1	-0.6	-0.5	1
1803	1950-11-20	HARROW	ONT	6130257	-82.9	42.03	182	1.3	1.7	-0.4	1
1804	1953-12-14	HARROW	ONT	6130257	-82.9	42.03	182	-0.1	0.6	-0.7	1
1805	1966-11-18	HARROW	ONT	6130257	-82.9	42.03	182	2.4	6.7	-4.3	1
1806	1966-11-27	HARROW	ONT	6130257	-82.9	42.03	182	1.7	5	-3.3	1
1807	2008-02-09	HARROW	ONT	6130257	-82.9	42.03	182	-6	-0.5	-5.5	1
1808	2011-03-23	HARROW	ONT	6130257	-82.9	42.03	182	-1.5	1	-2.5	1
1809	1925-02-11	REXTON	NB	8104400	-64.87	46.67	5	2.2	2.4	-0.2	1
1810	1926-02-02	REXTON	NB	8104400	-64.87	46.67	5	-11.1	-10.9	-0.2	1
1811	1926-04-06	REXTON	NB	8104400	-64.87	46.67	5	-0.6	4.1	-4.7	1
1812	1926-04-12	REXTON	NB	8104400	-64.87	46.67	5	-3.3	-1.1	-2.2	1
1813	1926-09-24	REXTON	NB	8104400	-64.87	46.67	5	13.3	14.1	-0.8	1
1814	1927-10-19	REXTON	NB	8104400	-64.87	46.67	5	12.8	13.6	-0.8	1
1815	1927-12-16	REXTON	NB	8104400	-64.87	46.67	5	-5	-0.4	-4.6	1
1816	1927-12-19	REXTON	NB	8104400	-64.87	46.67	5	-4.4	-0.4	-4	1
1817	1927-12-20	REXTON	NB	8104400	-64.87	46.67	5	1.7	4.1	-2.4	1
1818	1927-12-27	REXTON	NB	8104400	-64.87	46.67	5	-6.1	-6	-0.1	1
1819	1927-12-29	REXTON	NB	8104400	-64.87	46.67	5	1.1	5.4	-4.3	1
1820	1928-01-07	REXTON	NB	8104400	-64.87	46.67	5	-2.8	-1.7	-1.1	1
1821	1928-02-22	REXTON	NB	8104400	-64.87	46.67	5	-11.1	-0.4	-10.7	1
1822	1928-06-16	REXTON	NB	8104400	-64.87	46.67	5	12.2	12.5	-0.3	1
1823	1929-06-05	REXTON	NB	8104400	-64.87	46.67	5	10	10.4	-0.4	1
1824	1930-12-08	REXTON	NB	8104400	-64.87	46.67	5	0	0.7	-0.7	1
1825	1931-02-22	REXTON	NB	8104400	-64.87	46.67	5	0	0.7	-0.7	1
1826	1931-02-23	REXTON	NB	8104400	-64.87	46.67	5	-1.1	-0.8	-0.3	1
1827	1931-02-25	REXTON	NB	8104400	-64.87	46.67	5	1.1	1.9	-0.8	1
1828	1932-03-07	REXTON	NB	8104400	-64.87	46.67	5	0.6	0.7	-0.1	1
1829	1932-03-25	REXTON	NB	8104400	-64.87	46.67	5	0	0.7	-0.7	1
1830	1932-04-16	REXTON	NB	8104400	-64.87	46.67	5	1.7	1.9	-0.2	1
1831	1932-11-30	REXTON	NB	8104400	-64.87	46.67	5	1.1	1.9	-0.8	1
1832	1933-02-27	REXTON	NB	8104400	-64.87	46.67	5	1.1	1.3	-0.2	1
1833	1933-03-01	REXTON	NB	8104400	-64.87	46.67	5	0.6	0.7	-0.1	1
1834	1933-03-04	REXTON	NB	8104400	-64.87	46.67	5	-3.3	-2.9	-0.4	1
1835	1933-04-03	REXTON	NB	8104400	-64.87	46.67	5	2.2	2.5	-0.3	1

1836	1933-09-10	REXTON	NB	8104400	-64.87	46.67	5	15	15.4	-0.4	1
1837	1933-09-12	REXTON	NB	8104400	-64.87	46.67	5	14.4	14.6	-0.2	1
1838	1933-11-04	REXTON	NB	8104400	-64.87	46.67	5	5	6.3	-1.3	1
1839	1934-01-12	REXTON	NB	8104400	-64.87	46.67	5	-2.8	-2.4	-0.4	1
1840	1934-01-15	REXTON	NB	8104400	-64.87	46.67	5	-9.4	-8.6	-0.8	1
1841	1934-01-18	REXTON	NB	8104400	-64.87	46.67	5	-9.4	-8.2	-1.2	1
1842	1934-01-26	REXTON	NB	8104400	-64.87	46.67	5	-8.3	-7.6	-0.7	1
1843	1934-02-14	REXTON	NB	8104400	-64.87	46.67	5	-14.4	-12.9	-1.5	1
1844	1934-02-24	REXTON	NB	8104400	-64.87	46.67	5	-13.3	-11.9	-1.4	1
1845	1934-04-08	REXTON	NB	8104400	-64.87	46.67	5	1.1	1.2	-0.1	1
1846	1934-10-22	REXTON	NB	8104400	-64.87	46.67	5	6.7	6.9	-0.2	1
1847	1934-10-25	REXTON	NB	8104400	-64.87	46.67	5	7.2	8	-0.8	1
1848	1934-11-18	REXTON	NB	8104400	-64.87	46.67	5	1.7	1.9	-0.2	1
1849	1934-11-20	REXTON	NB	8104400	-64.87	46.67	5	0.6	1.9	-1.3	1
1850	1935-02-16	REXTON	NB	8104400	-64.87	46.67	5	-3.9	-2.9	-1	1
1851	1935-02-22	REXTON	NB	8104400	-64.87	46.67	5	-13.9	-12.4	-1.5	1
1852	1935-02-27	REXTON	NB	8104400	-64.87	46.67	5	-11.1	-10.9	-0.2	1
1853	1935-03-06	REXTON	NB	8104400	-64.87	46.67	5	-10.6	-10.4	-0.2	1
1854	1935-04-18	REXTON	NB	8104400	-64.87	46.67	5	0.6	1.9	-1.3	1
1855	1935-04-21	REXTON	NB	8104400	-64.87	46.67	5	1.7	2.5	-0.8	1
1856	1935-11-14	REXTON	NB	8104400	-64.87	46.67	5	4.4	4.8	-0.4	1
1857	1935-12-11	REXTON	NB	8104400	-64.87	46.67	5	0.6	0.7	-0.1	1
1858	1935-12-28	REXTON	NB	8104400	-64.87	46.67	5	-7.8	-7.2	-0.6	1
1859	1936-05-03	REXTON	NB	8104400	-64.87	46.67	5	3.3	3.5	-0.2	1
1860	1936-05-28	REXTON	NB	8104400	-64.87	46.67	5	10	10.3	-0.3	1
1861	1936-08-23	REXTON	NB	8104400	-64.87	46.67	5	15.6	15.7	-0.1	1
1862	1936-10-23	REXTON	NB	8104400	-64.87	46.67	5	8.3	8.5	-0.2	1
1863	1936-11-18	REXTON	NB	8104400	-64.87	46.67	5	-9.4	-8.2	-1.2	1
1864	1936-11-23	REXTON	NB	8104400	-64.87	46.67	5	0	0.7	-0.7	1
1865	1936-12-04	REXTON	NB	8104400	-64.87	46.67	5	-1.1	-0.8	-0.3	1
1866	1936-12-12	REXTON	NB	8104400	-64.87	46.67	5	3.3	3.8	-0.5	1
1867	1937-01-19	REXTON	NB	8104400	-64.87	46.67	5	1.7	2.5	-0.8	1
1868	1937-05-14	REXTON	NB	8104400	-64.87	46.67	5	5.6	5.7	-0.1	1
1869	1937-10-02	REXTON	NB	8104400	-64.87	46.67	5	4.4	4.8	-0.4	1

1870	1937-12-29	REXTON	NB	8104400	-64.87	46.67	5	-10	-8.2	-1.8	1
1871	1938-01-08	REXTON	NB	8104400	-64.87	46.67	5	-5	-4.7	-0.3	1
1872	1938-02-07	REXTON	NB	8104400	-64.87	46.67	5	-1.1	0	-1.1	1
1873	1938-04-21	REXTON	NB	8104400	-64.87	46.67	5	8.3	8.5	-0.2	1
1874	1938-05-15	REXTON	NB	8104400	-64.87	46.67	5	8.9	9.1	-0.2	1
1875	1938-10-06	REXTON	NB	8104400	-64.87	46.67	5	7.8	8	-0.2	1
1876	1938-11-20	REXTON	NB	8104400	-64.87	46.67	5	0	0.7	-0.7	1
1877	1938-12-10	REXTON	NB	8104400	-64.87	46.67	5	2.8	2.9	-0.1	1
1878	1938-12-13	REXTON	NB	8104400	-64.87	46.67	5	0	0.7	-0.7	1
1879	1939-01-12	REXTON	NB	8104400	-64.87	46.67	5	-9.4	-8.6	-0.8	1
1880	1939-03-11	REXTON	NB	8104400	-64.87	46.67	5	-17.2	-16	-1.2	1
1881	1939-11-23	REXTON	NB	8104400	-64.87	46.67	5	-1.1	0.7	-1.8	1
1882	1939-12-05	REXTON	NB	8104400	-64.87	46.67	5	-0.6	0	-0.6	1
1883	1939-12-14	REXTON	NB	8104400	-64.87	46.67	5	-5.6	-5.1	-0.5	1
1884	1939-12-17	REXTON	NB	8104400	-64.87	46.67	5	1.7	1.9	-0.2	1
1885	1940-03-07	REXTON	NB	8104400	-64.87	46.67	5	0.6	0.7	-0.1	1
1886	1940-03-31	REXTON	NB	8104400	-64.87	46.67	5	2.8	2.9	-0.1	1
1887	1940-04-01	REXTON	NB	8104400	-64.87	46.67	5	1.7	1.9	-0.2	1
1888	1940-04-21	REXTON	NB	8104400	-64.87	46.67	5	1.7	1.9	-0.2	1
1889	1940-04-22	REXTON	NB	8104400	-64.87	46.67	5	1.1	1.3	-0.2	1
1890	1940-04-23	REXTON	NB	8104400	-64.87	46.67	5	0.6	0.7	-0.1	1
1891	1940-06-09	REXTON	NB	8104400	-64.87	46.67	5	13.3	13.5	-0.2	1
1892	1940-09-25	REXTON	NB	8104400	-64.87	46.67	5	11.7	12.8	-1.1	1
1893	1940-12-09	REXTON	NB	8104400	-64.87	46.67	5	0.6	0.7	-0.1	1
1894	1940-12-31	REXTON	NB	8104400	-64.87	46.67	5	0.6	1.3	-0.7	1
1895	1941-03-26	REXTON	NB	8104400	-64.87	46.67	5	4.4	4.8	-0.4	1
1896	1941-08-03	REXTON	NB	8104400	-64.87	46.67	5	16.1	16.2	-0.1	1
1897	1942-03-26	REXTON	NB	8104400	-64.87	46.67	5	1.1	1.9	-0.8	1
1898	1942-03-27	REXTON	NB	8104400	-64.87	46.67	5	-0.6	-0.1	-0.5	1
1899	1942-03-31	REXTON	NB	8104400	-64.87	46.67	5	-1.1	-0.1	-1	1
1900	1942-04-12	REXTON	NB	8104400	-64.87	46.67	5	0	0.7	-0.7	1
1901	1942-04-26	REXTON	NB	8104400	-64.87	46.67	5	3.3	4.4	-1.1	1
1902	1942-05-01	REXTON	NB	8104400	-64.87	46.67	5	6.1	6.9	-0.8	1
1903	1942-06-17	REXTON	NB	8104400	-64.87	46.67	5	15.6	15.8	-0.2	1

1904	1942-11-28	REXTON	NB	8104400	-64.87	46.67	5	-0.6	0.7	-1.3	1
1905	1942-12-14	REXTON	NB	8104400	-64.87	46.67	5	-9.4	-8.6	-0.8	1
1906	1942-12-19	REXTON	NB	8104400	-64.87	46.67	5	-21.7	-21	-0.7	1
1907	1943-10-25	REXTON	NB	8104400	-64.87	46.67	5	6.7	6.9	-0.2	1
1908	1943-11-04	REXTON	NB	8104400	-64.87	46.67	5	4.4	4.8	-0.4	1
1909	1943-11-22	REXTON	NB	8104400	-64.87	46.67	5	3.9	4.4	-0.5	1
1910	1944-01-27	REXTON	NB	8104400	-64.87	46.67	5	0	0.7	-0.7	1
1911	1944-02-18	REXTON	NB	8104400	-64.87	46.67	5	0.6	0.7	-0.1	1
1912	1944-06-13	REXTON	NB	8104400	-64.87	46.67	5	9.4	9.6	-0.2	1
1913	1944-11-12	REXTON	NB	8104400	-64.87	46.67	5	1.7	2.4	-0.7	1
1914	1944-11-23	REXTON	NB	8104400	-64.87	46.67	5	3.9	4.3	-0.4	1
1915	1944-12-11	REXTON	NB	8104400	-64.87	46.67	5	0	0.7	-0.7	1
1916	1945-01-09	REXTON	NB	8104400	-64.87	46.67	5	-3.9	-3.8	-0.1	1
1917	1945-01-24	REXTON	NB	8104400	-64.87	46.67	5	-6.7	-5.7	-1	1
1918	1945-03-04	REXTON	NB	8104400	-64.87	46.67	5	-1.1	-0.7	-0.4	1
1919	1945-04-03	REXTON	NB	8104400	-64.87	46.67	5	-1.7	-0.7	-1	1
1920	1945-05-11	REXTON	NB	8104400	-64.87	46.67	5	4.4	4.8	-0.4	1
1921	1945-10-24	REXTON	NB	8104400	-64.87	46.67	5	5	5.3	-0.3	1
1922	1945-11-15	REXTON	NB	8104400	-64.87	46.67	5	3.3	3.4	-0.1	1
1923	1945-12-12	REXTON	NB	8104400	-64.87	46.67	5	-11.1	-10.4	-0.7	1
1924	1946-02-08	REXTON	NB	8104400	-64.87	46.67	5	-3.9	-2.8	-1.1	1
1925	1946-04-23	REXTON	NB	8104400	-64.87	46.67	5	1.7	1.9	-0.2	1
1926	1946-10-30	REXTON	NB	8104400	-64.87	46.67	5	4.4	4.7	-0.3	1
1927	1946-11-28	REXTON	NB	8104400	-64.87	46.67	5	2.8	3.4	-0.6	1
1928	1946-12-27	REXTON	NB	8104400	-64.87	46.67	5	-21.1	-21	-0.1	1
1929	1947-02-09	REXTON	NB	8104400	-64.87	46.67	5	-3.9	-2.9	-1	1
1930	1947-02-19	REXTON	NB	8104400	-64.87	46.67	5	-0.6	-0.1	-0.5	1
1931	1947-04-12	REXTON	NB	8104400	-64.87	46.67	5	1.1	1.9	-0.8	1
1932	1947-07-12	REXTON	NB	8104400	-64.87	46.67	5	21.1	21.5	-0.4	1
1933	1948-12-30	REXTON	NB	8104400	-64.87	46.67	5	1.7	1.9	-0.2	1
1934	1949-04-17	REXTON	NB	8104400	-64.87	46.67	5	2.2	2.4	-0.2	1
1935	1950-01-05	REXTON	NB	8104400	-64.87	46.67	5	7.8	8.5	-0.7	1
1936	1951-02-23	REXTON	NB	8104400	-64.87	46.67	5	1.7	1.9	-0.2	1
1937	1952-10-24	REXTON	NB	8104400	-64.87	46.67	5	8.3	8.5	-0.2	1

1938	1954-11-12	REXTON	NB	8104400	-64.87	46.67	5	0	0.6	-0.6	1
1939	1954-12-10	REXTON	NB	8104400	-64.87	46.67	5	2.2	2.5	-0.3	1
1940	1954-12-17	REXTON	NB	8104400	-64.87	46.67	5	2.2	2.5	-0.3	1
1941	1955-03-17	REXTON	NB	8104400	-64.87	46.67	5	-2.2	-1.4	-0.8	1
1942	1955-05-10	REXTON	NB	8104400	-64.87	46.67	5	7.2	7.4	-0.2	1
1943	1956-01-14	REXTON	NB	8104400	-64.87	46.67	5	1.1	1.9	-0.8	1
1944	1956-01-17	REXTON	NB	8104400	-64.87	46.67	5	1.1	1.9	-0.8	1
1945	1956-12-18	REXTON	NB	8104400	-64.87	46.67	5	-5.6	-4.7	-0.9	1
1946	1957-02-12	REXTON	NB	8104400	-64.87	46.67	5	-11.1	-10.4	-0.7	1
1947	1957-12-08	REXTON	NB	8104400	-64.87	46.67	5	1.7	1.9	-0.2	1
1948	1958-01-19	REXTON	NB	8104400	-64.87	46.67	5	3.3	3.5	-0.2	1
1949	1958-01-28	REXTON	NB	8104400	-64.87	46.67	5	0	0.6	-0.6	1
1950	1958-03-12	REXTON	NB	8104400	-64.87	46.67	5	1.7	1.9	-0.2	1
1951	1958-03-16	REXTON	NB	8104400	-64.87	46.67	5	-1.1	-0.7	-0.4	1
1952	1958-11-29	REXTON	NB	8104400	-64.87	46.67	5	1.7	1.9	-0.2	1
1953	1959-02-11	REXTON	NB	8104400	-64.87	46.67	5	-12.2	-11.9	-0.3	1
1954	1959-04-07	REXTON	NB	8104400	-64.87	46.67	5	2.8	3.4	-0.6	1
1955	1959-04-11	REXTON	NB	8104400	-64.87	46.67	5	1.7	1.9	-0.2	1
1956	1959-05-03	REXTON	NB	8104400	-64.87	46.67	5	4.4	4.8	-0.4	1
1957	1959-05-05	REXTON	NB	8104400	-64.87	46.67	5	4.4	5.3	-0.9	1
1958	1959-11-30	REXTON	NB	8104400	-64.87	46.67	5	-5	-4.7	-0.3	1
1959	1959-12-04	REXTON	NB	8104400	-64.87	46.67	5	2.2	2.9	-0.7	1
1960	1959-12-08	REXTON	NB	8104400	-64.87	46.67	5	4.4	4.8	-0.4	1
1961	1959-12-17	REXTON	NB	8104400	-64.87	46.67	5	-1.1	-0.7	-0.4	1
1962	1960-01-22	REXTON	NB	8104400	-64.87	46.67	5	-1.1	-0.7	-0.4	1
1963	1960-01-23	REXTON	NB	8104400	-64.87	46.67	5	-1.7	-0.7	-1	1
1964	1960-01-24	REXTON	NB	8104400	-64.87	46.67	5	-3.9	-3.3	-0.6	1
1965	1960-02-15	REXTON	NB	8104400	-64.87	46.67	5	0.6	0.7	-0.1	1
1966	1960-03-23	REXTON	NB	8104400	-64.87	46.67	5	-2.2	-1.9	-0.3	1
1967	1960-12-17	REXTON	NB	8104400	-64.87	46.67	5	1.7	1.9	-0.2	1
1968	1960-12-27	REXTON	NB	8104400	-64.87	46.67	5	-3.9	-3.8	-0.1	1
1969	1961-01-05	REXTON	NB	8104400	-64.87	46.67	5	-9.4	-8.7	-0.7	1
1970	1961-01-19	REXTON	NB	8104400	-64.87	46.67	5	-18.9	-18.8	-0.1	1
1971	1961-02-10	REXTON	NB	8104400	-64.87	46.67	5	-6.7	-6.1	-0.6	1

1972	1961-10-21	REXTON	NB	8104400	-64.87	46.67	5	7.8	8	-0.2	1
1973	1961-11-26	REXTON	NB	8104400	-64.87	46.67	5	7.2	7.4	-0.2	1
1974	1961-11-27	REXTON	NB	8104400	-64.87	46.67	5	6.1	6.9	-0.8	1
1975	1962-07-06	REXTON	NB	8104400	-64.87	46.67	5	11.7	12.3	-0.6	1
1976	1962-08-10	REXTON	NB	8104400	-64.87	46.67	5	14.4	15.3	-0.9	1
1977	1962-09-12	REXTON	NB	8104400	-64.87	46.67	5	15	15.7	-0.7	1
1978	1962-11-16	REXTON	NB	8104400	-64.87	46.67	5	3.9	4.3	-0.4	1
1979	1962-11-23	REXTON	NB	8104400	-64.87	46.67	5	2.8	2.9	-0.1	1
1980	1963-06-04	REXTON	NB	8104400	-64.87	46.67	5	14.4	14.5	-0.1	1
1981	1964-03-10	REXTON	NB	8104400	-64.87	46.67	5	-6.7	-6.1	-0.6	1
1982	1964-12-06	REXTON	NB	8104400	-64.87	46.67	5	-3.9	-3.4	-0.5	1
1983	1964-12-31	REXTON	NB	8104400	-64.87	46.67	5	0.6	0.7	-0.1	1
1984	1965-01-01	REXTON	NB	8104400	-64.87	46.67	5	0	0.7	-0.7	1
1985	1965-01-10	REXTON	NB	8104400	-64.87	46.67	5	-10.6	-10.4	-0.2	1
1986	1965-01-28	REXTON	NB	8104400	-64.87	46.67	5	-7.2	-7.1	-0.1	1
1987	1965-01-29	REXTON	NB	8104400	-64.87	46.67	5	-11.7	-11.4	-0.3	1
1988	1965-03-05	REXTON	NB	8104400	-64.87	46.67	5	3.3	3.4	-0.1	1
1989	1965-03-06	REXTON	NB	8104400	-64.87	46.67	5	2.2	2.4	-0.2	1
1990	1965-05-14	REXTON	NB	8104400	-64.87	46.67	5	5.6	5.8	-0.2	1
1991	1965-11-19	REXTON	NB	8104400	-64.87	46.67	5	-1.1	-0.2	-0.9	1
1992	1966-01-09	REXTON	NB	8104400	-64.87	46.67	5	-6.7	-6.1	-0.6	1
1993	1966-01-21	REXTON	NB	8104400	-64.87	46.67	5	-1.1	-0.8	-0.3	1
1994	1966-12-02	REXTON	NB	8104400	-64.87	46.67	5	1.7	2.5	-0.8	1
1995	1967-01-03	REXTON	NB	8104400	-64.87	46.67	5	-1.7	-0.1	-1.6	1
1996	1967-01-06	REXTON	NB	8104400	-64.87	46.67	5	-4.4	-4.2	-0.2	1
1997	1967-02-03	REXTON	NB	8104400	-64.87	46.67	5	-10	-9.1	-0.9	1
1998	1967-02-06	REXTON	NB	8104400	-64.87	46.67	5	-11.7	-10	-1.7	1
1999	1967-02-12	REXTON	NB	8104400	-64.87	46.67	5	-20.6	-18.8	-1.8	1
2000	1967-03-01	REXTON	NB	8104400	-64.87	46.67	5	-3.9	-3.4	-0.5	1
2001	1967-03-30	REXTON	NB	8104400	-64.87	46.67	5	-3.3	-2.5	-0.8	1
2002	1967-12-10	REXTON	NB	8104400	-64.87	46.67	5	-6.1	-5.6	-0.5	1
2003	1967-12-24	REXTON	NB	8104400	-64.87	46.67	5	-9.4	-8.2	-1.2	1
2004	1968-01-16	REXTON	NB	8104400	-64.87	46.67	5	-11.7	-10	-1.7	1
2005	1968-03-18	REXTON	NB	8104400	-64.87	46.67	5	2.2	2.5	-0.3	1

2006	1968-03-21	REXTON	NB	8104400	-64.87	46.67	5	0.6	1.3	-0.7	1
2007	1968-03-31	REXTON	NB	8104400	-64.87	46.67	5	0.6	1.9	-1.3	1
2008	1968-04-18	REXTON	NB	8104400	-64.87	46.67	5	3.3	3.5	-0.2	1
2009	1968-04-19	REXTON	NB	8104400	-64.87	46.67	5	2.2	2.5	-0.3	1
2010	1968-04-20	REXTON	NB	8104400	-64.87	46.67	5	2.2	2.9	-0.7	1
2011	1968-09-24	REXTON	NB	8104400	-64.87	46.67	5	14.4	14.5	-0.1	1
2012	1968-12-17	REXTON	NB	8104400	-64.87	46.67	5	-1.1	-0.1	-1	1
2013	1968-12-21	REXTON	NB	8104400	-64.87	46.67	5	0	0.7	-0.7	1
2014	1968-12-25	REXTON	NB	8104400	-64.87	46.67	5	-8.3	-7.7	-0.6	1
2015	1969-03-12	REXTON	NB	8104400	-64.87	46.67	5	1.7	2.5	-0.8	1
2016	1969-03-30	REXTON	NB	8104400	-64.87	46.67	5	-3.9	-3.4	-0.5	1
2017	1969-04-19	REXTON	NB	8104400	-64.87	46.67	5	1.1	1.9	-0.8	1
2018	1969-06-16	REXTON	NB	8104400	-64.87	46.67	5	12.2	12.8	-0.6	1
2019	1969-10-04	REXTON	NB	8104400	-64.87	46.67	5	8.9	9.1	-0.2	1
2020	1969-12-05	REXTON	NB	8104400	-64.87	46.67	5	-1.7	-1.4	-0.3	1
2021	1969-12-29	REXTON	NB	8104400	-64.87	46.67	5	1.7	2.5	-0.8	1
2022	1970-06-01	REXTON	NB	8104400	-64.87	46.67	5	12.8	13.5	-0.7	1
2023	1970-07-01	REXTON	NB	8104400	-64.87	46.67	5	14.4	14.5	-0.1	1
2024	1970-10-26	REXTON	NB	8104400	-64.87	46.67	5	5	5.3	-0.3	1
2025	1970-11-23	REXTON	NB	8104400	-64.87	46.67	5	1.1	1.3	-0.2	1
2026	1970-12-23	REXTON	NB	8104400	-64.87	46.67	5	-21.1	-20.5	-0.6	1
2027	1971-01-06	REXTON	NB	8104400	-64.87	46.67	5	-3.3	-2.4	-0.9	1
2028	1971-01-12	REXTON	NB	8104400	-64.87	46.67	5	-9.4	-8.2	-1.2	1
2029	1971-01-28	REXTON	NB	8104400	-64.87	46.67	5	-18.9	-17.7	-1.2	1
2030	1971-02-15	REXTON	NB	8104400	-64.87	46.67	5	-3.9	-2.9	-1	1
2031	1971-04-19	REXTON	NB	8104400	-64.87	46.67	5	1.7	2.5	-0.8	1
2032	1971-04-21	REXTON	NB	8104400	-64.87	46.67	5	2.8	2.9	-0.1	1
2033	1971-05-27	REXTON	NB	8104400	-64.87	46.67	5	8.3	8.5	-0.2	1
2034	1971-09-05	REXTON	NB	8104400	-64.87	46.67	5	14.4	14.9	-0.5	1
2035	1971-11-27	REXTON	NB	8104400	-64.87	46.67	5	0.6	0.7	-0.1	1
2036	1971-12-01	REXTON	NB	8104400	-64.87	46.67	5	-4.4	-3.3	-1.1	1
2037	1971-12-12	REXTON	NB	8104400	-64.87	46.67	5	1.7	1.9	-0.2	1
2038	1971-12-22	REXTON	NB	8104400	-64.87	46.67	5	-7.2	-5.7	-1.5	1
2039	1972-01-04	REXTON	NB	8104400	-64.87	46.67	5	-4.4	-4.2	-0.2	1

2040	1972-01-24	REXTON	NB	8104400	-64.87	46.67	5	-0.6	-0.2	-0.4	1
2041	1972-03-04	REXTON	NB	8104400	-64.87	46.67	5	-12.2	-12	-0.2	1
2042	1972-03-29	REXTON	NB	8104400	-64.87	46.67	5	1.1	1.3	-0.2	1
2043	1974-10-30	REXTON	NB	8104400	-64.87	46.67	5	4.4	4.5	-0.1	1
2044	1984-02-07	REXTON	NB	8104400	-64.87	46.67	5	-10	-9.7	-0.3	1
2045	1984-02-26	REXTON	NB	8104400	-64.87	46.67	5	-1	-0.6	-0.4	1
2046	1984-03-30	REXTON	NB	8104400	-64.87	46.67	5	-1	-0.6	-0.4	1
2047	1984-04-26	REXTON	NB	8104400	-64.87	46.67	5	1	1.3	-0.3	1
2048	1984-06-03	REXTON	NB	8104400	-64.87	46.67	5	8	8.3	-0.3	1
2049	1984-07-05	REXTON	NB	8104400	-64.87	46.67	5	20	20.4	-0.4	1
2050	1985-06-06	REXTON	NB	8104400	-64.87	46.67	5	10	10.2	-0.2	1
2051	1985-11-02	REXTON	NB	8104400	-64.87	46.67	5	5	5.5	-0.5	1
2052	1985-11-03	REXTON	NB	8104400	-64.87	46.67	5	6	6.4	-0.4	1
2053	1986-07-31	REXTON	NB	8104400	-64.87	46.67	5	15	15.8	-0.8	1
2054	1987-03-19	REXTON	NB	8104400	-64.87	46.67	5	1	1.2	-0.2	1
2055	1987-04-07	REXTON	NB	8104400	-64.87	46.67	5	1	1.2	-0.2	1
2056	1987-04-08	REXTON	NB	8104400	-64.87	46.67	5	0	1.2	-1.2	1
2057	1987-12-13	REXTON	NB	8104400	-64.87	46.67	5	-2	-1.6	-0.4	1
2058	1990-01-30	REXTON	NB	8104400	-64.87	46.67	5	-5	-4.9	-0.1	1
2059	1990-11-18	REXTON	NB	8104400	-64.87	46.67	5	1	1.2	-0.2	1
2060	1990-12-17	REXTON	NB	8104400	-64.87	46.67	5	1	1.2	-0.2	1
2061	1990-12-22	REXTON	NB	8104400	-64.87	46.67	5	1	1.2	-0.2	1
2062	1991-03-08	REXTON	NB	8104400	-64.87	46.67	5	1	1.1	-0.1	1
2063	1991-03-11	REXTON	NB	8104400	-64.87	46.67	5	-1	0.2	-1.2	1
2064	1991-03-13	REXTON	NB	8104400	-64.87	46.67	5	1	1.1	-0.1	1
2065	1994-03-05	REXTON	NB	8104400	-64.87	46.67	5	-4	-3.9	-0.1	1
2066	1994-03-11	REXTON	NB	8104400	-64.87	46.67	5	-1	-0.7	-0.3	1
2067	1996-02-10	REXTON	NB	8104400	-64.87	46.67	5	-2.5	-2.2	-0.3	1
2068	2006-03-01	REXTON	NB	8104400	-64.87	46.67	5	11	16.5	-5.5	1
2069	2006-03-02	REXTON	NB	8104400	-64.87	46.67	5	10.5	19.5	-9	1
2070	2006-03-03	REXTON	NB	8104400	-64.87	46.67	5	4	14.5	-10.5	1
2071	2006-03-04	REXTON	NB	8104400	-64.87	46.67	5	0.5	4.5	-4	1
2072	2008-02-18	REXTON	NB	8104400	-64.87	46.67	5	-10	-8	-2	1
2073	2008-02-19	REXTON	NB	8104400	-64.87	46.67	5	-4	-2	-2	1

2074	2008-12-29	REXTON	NB	8104400	-64.87	46.67	5	1.5	3	-1.5	1
2075	1915-11-26	UPPER STEWACKE	NS	8204193	-63	45.22	24	5.9	6.1	-0.2	1
2076	1915-11-27	UPPER STEWACKE	NS	8204193	-63	45.22	24	7.9	8.3	-0.4	1
2077	1979-11-04	UPPER STEWACKE	NS	8204193	-63	45.22	24	6	7	-1	1
2078	1934-01-26	DEER LAKE	NFLD	8401502	-57.4	49.22	22	-2.2	-1.7	-0.5	1
2079	1958-11-17	DEER LAKE	NFLD	8401502	-57.4	49.22	22	-2.2	-1.7	-0.5	1
2080	1979-09-29	DEER LAKE	NFLD	8401502	-57.4	49.22	22	1.1	5.4	-4.3	1
2081	1989-10-13	DEER LAKE	NFLD	8401502	-57.4	49.22	22	8.3	9.7	-1.4	1
2082	2017-11-24	DEER LAKE	NFLD	8401502	-57.4	49.22	22	2.2	4.7	-2.5	1
2083	2019-09-25	DEER LAKE	NFLD	8401502	-57.4	49.22	22	8.7	8.9	-0.2	1
2084	1908-08-14	PRINCE RUPERT	BC	1066482	-130.45	54.28	35	12.6	12.7	-0.1	1
2085	1908-12-26	PRINCE RUPERT	BC	1066482	-130.45	54.28	35	0.8	1.1	-0.3	1
2086	1909-05-20	PRINCE RUPERT	BC	1066482	-130.45	54.28	35	4.9	5.3	-0.4	1
2087	1909-07-29	PRINCE RUPERT	BC	1066482	-130.45	54.28	35	13.1	13.4	-0.3	1
2088	1909-10-08	PRINCE RUPERT	BC	1066482	-130.45	54.28	35	4.1	4.7	-0.6	1
2089	1909-10-15	PRINCE RUPERT	BC	1066482	-130.45	54.28	35	4.8	5.7	-0.9	1
2090	1909-10-26	PRINCE RUPERT	BC	1066482	-130.45	54.28	35	4.8	5.3	-0.5	1
2091	1909-11-18	PRINCE RUPERT	BC	1066482	-130.45	54.28	35	4.1	5.3	-1.2	1
2092	1910-01-15	PRINCE RUPERT	BC	1066482	-130.45	54.28	35	0.4	1	-0.6	1
2093	1910-10-20	PRINCE RUPERT	BC	1066482	-130.45	54.28	35	5.7	6.5	-0.8	1
2094	1910-10-22	PRINCE RUPERT	BC	1066482	-130.45	54.28	35	6.9	7.9	-1	1
2095	1910-11-02	PRINCE RUPERT	BC	1066482	-130.45	54.28	35	3.5	3.8	-0.3	1
2096	1910-11-04	PRINCE RUPERT	BC	1066482	-130.45	54.28	35	4.1	5.3	-1.2	1
2097	1910-11-20	PRINCE RUPERT	BC	1066482	-130.45	54.28	35	5.7	6.5	-0.8	1
2098	1910-11-22	PRINCE RUPERT	BC	1066482	-130.45	54.28	35	2.5	3.1	-0.6	1
2099	1910-12-09	PRINCE RUPERT	BC	1066482	-130.45	54.28	35	0.5	1	-0.5	1
2100	1910-12-16	PRINCE RUPERT	BC	1066482	-130.45	54.28	35	2.5	3.9	-1.4	1
2101	1910-12-23	PRINCE RUPERT	BC	1066482	-130.45	54.28	35	2.5	3.3	-0.8	1
2102	1910-12-29	PRINCE RUPERT	BC	1066482	-130.45	54.28	35	1.2	1.6	-0.4	1
2103	1911-01-04	PRINCE RUPERT	BC	1066482	-130.45	54.28	35	2.5	3.9	-1.4	1
2104	1911-02-17	PRINCE RUPERT	BC	1066482	-130.45	54.28	35	5	5.2	-0.2	1
2105	1911-02-23	PRINCE RUPERT	BC	1066482	-130.45	54.28	35	0.2	1.7	-1.5	1
2106	1911-03-06	PRINCE RUPERT	BC	1066482	-130.45	54.28	35	0.6	1	-0.4	1
2107	1911-03-09	PRINCE RUPERT	BC	1066482	-130.45	54.28	35	0.4	0.6	-0.2	1

2108	1911-03-10	PRINCE RUPERT	BC	1066482	-130.45	54.28	35	0	0.6	-0.6	1
2109	1911-03-13	PRINCE RUPERT	BC	1066482	-130.45	54.28	35	1.3	1.4	-0.1	1
2110	1911-03-19	PRINCE RUPERT	BC	1066482	-130.45	54.28	35	0.2	1	-0.8	1
2111	1911-03-27	PRINCE RUPERT	BC	1066482	-130.45	54.28	35	0.8	1	-0.2	1
2112	1911-04-20	PRINCE RUPERT	BC	1066482	-130.45	54.28	35	3.5	4.7	-1.2	1
2113	1911-06-03	PRINCE RUPERT	BC	1066482	-130.45	54.28	35	5	6.5	-1.5	1
2114	1911-06-08	PRINCE RUPERT	BC	1066482	-130.45	54.28	35	6.9	8	-1.1	1
2115	1911-07-22	PRINCE RUPERT	BC	1066482	-130.45	54.28	35	12.2	12.7	-0.5	1
2116	1911-07-24	PRINCE RUPERT	BC	1066482	-130.45	54.28	35	11.8	12.7	-0.9	1
2117	1911-08-30	PRINCE RUPERT	BC	1066482	-130.45	54.28	35	12.6	12.7	-0.1	1
2118	1911-11-02	PRINCE RUPERT	BC	1066482	-130.45	54.28	35	8.4	8.5	-0.1	1
2119	1911-11-03	PRINCE RUPERT	BC	1066482	-130.45	54.28	35	6.4	7.2	-0.8	1
2120	1911-11-04	PRINCE RUPERT	BC	1066482	-130.45	54.28	35	5.6	5.7	-0.1	1
2121	1911-11-18	PRINCE RUPERT	BC	1066482	-130.45	54.28	35	4.9	5.2	-0.3	1
2122	1911-11-28	PRINCE RUPERT	BC	1066482	-130.45	54.28	35	4.9	5.7	-0.8	1
2123	1911-12-04	PRINCE RUPERT	BC	1066482	-130.45	54.28	35	5.6	6.5	-0.9	1
2124	1911-12-08	PRINCE RUPERT	BC	1066482	-130.45	54.28	35	5.1	6.5	-1.4	1
2125	1911-12-22	PRINCE RUPERT	BC	1066482	-130.45	54.28	35	0.3	0.6	-0.3	1
2126	1912-01-29	PRINCE RUPERT	BC	1066482	-130.45	54.28	35	5	5.3	-0.3	1
2127	1912-02-15	PRINCE RUPERT	BC	1066482	-130.45	54.28	35	4.1	5.3	-1.2	1
2128	1912-02-20	PRINCE RUPERT	BC	1066482	-130.45	54.28	35	2.9	4.7	-1.8	1
2129	1912-03-30	PRINCE RUPERT	BC	1066482	-130.45	54.28	35	4.1	4.7	-0.6	1
2130	1912-05-07	PRINCE RUPERT	BC	1066482	-130.45	54.28	35	6.3	7.2	-0.9	1
2131	1912-07-21	PRINCE RUPERT	BC	1066482	-130.45	54.28	35	11.8	12.8	-1	1
2132	1912-08-10	PRINCE RUPERT	BC	1066482	-130.45	54.28	35	12.6	12.7	-0.1	1
2133	1912-09-10	PRINCE RUPERT	BC	1066482	-130.45	54.28	35	14.4	14.5	-0.1	1
2134	1912-09-24	PRINCE RUPERT	BC	1066482	-130.45	54.28	35	8.4	8.8	-0.4	1
2135	1912-09-29	PRINCE RUPERT	BC	1066482	-130.45	54.28	35	12.1	12.8	-0.7	1
2136	1912-10-23	PRINCE RUPERT	BC	1066482	-130.45	54.28	35	3	3.2	-0.2	1
2137	1912-11-13	PRINCE RUPERT	BC	1066482	-130.45	54.28	35	5	5.7	-0.7	1
2138	1912-11-14	PRINCE RUPERT	BC	1066482	-130.45	54.28	35	5	5.3	-0.3	1
2139	1912-12-07	PRINCE RUPERT	BC	1066482	-130.45	54.28	35	6.9	8	-1.1	1
2140	1912-12-27	PRINCE RUPERT	BC	1066482	-130.45	54.28	35	0.2	0.6	-0.4	1
2141	1913-01-28	PRINCE RUPERT	BC	1066482	-130.45	54.28	35	1.2	1.3	-0.1	1

2142	1913-02-09	PRINCE RUPERT	BC	1066482	-130.45	54.28	35	0.1	0.2	-0.1	1
2143	1913-03-01	PRINCE RUPERT	BC	1066482	-130.45	54.28	35	0.9	1.1	-0.2	1
2144	1913-03-03	PRINCE RUPERT	BC	1066482	-130.45	54.28	35	5.7	7.3	-1.6	1
2145	1913-03-27	PRINCE RUPERT	BC	1066482	-130.45	54.28	35	1.2	1.3	-0.1	1
2146	1913-03-31	PRINCE RUPERT	BC	1066482	-130.45	54.28	35	1.2	1.3	-0.1	1
2147	1913-04-21	PRINCE RUPERT	BC	1066482	-130.45	54.28	35	3.5	4	-0.5	1
2148	1913-07-15	PRINCE RUPERT	BC	1066482	-130.45	54.28	35	10.9	11.4	-0.5	1
2149	1913-07-27	PRINCE RUPERT	BC	1066482	-130.45	54.28	35	12.1	12.8	-0.7	1
2150	1913-08-14	PRINCE RUPERT	BC	1066482	-130.45	54.28	35	11.8	12.2	-0.4	1
2151	1913-08-23	PRINCE RUPERT	BC	1066482	-130.45	54.28	35	14.8	15.6	-0.8	1
2152	1913-09-07	PRINCE RUPERT	BC	1066482	-130.45	54.28	35	9.2	9.7	-0.5	1
2153	1913-09-12	PRINCE RUPERT	BC	1066482	-130.45	54.28	35	13.2	13.9	-0.7	1
2154	1913-09-28	PRINCE RUPERT	BC	1066482	-130.45	54.28	35	12.1	12.8	-0.7	1
2155	1913-09-29	PRINCE RUPERT	BC	1066482	-130.45	54.28	35	10.2	10.6	-0.4	1
2156	1913-10-11	PRINCE RUPERT	BC	1066482	-130.45	54.28	35	4.8	6.4	-1.6	1
2157	1913-10-14	PRINCE RUPERT	BC	1066482	-130.45	54.28	35	1.9	2.2	-0.3	1
2158	1913-11-03	PRINCE RUPERT	BC	1066482	-130.45	54.28	35	3.5	5.3	-1.8	1
2159	1913-11-13	PRINCE RUPERT	BC	1066482	-130.45	54.28	35	1.9	3.2	-1.3	1
2160	1913-11-19	PRINCE RUPERT	BC	1066482	-130.45	54.28	35	1.2	1.3	-0.1	1
2161	1913-12-17	PRINCE RUPERT	BC	1066482	-130.45	54.28	35	3.5	5.3	-1.8	1
2162	1914-01-04	PRINCE RUPERT	BC	1066482	-130.45	54.28	35	6.3	6.4	-0.1	1
2163	1914-01-11	PRINCE RUPERT	BC	1066482	-130.45	54.28	35	4.9	5.3	-0.4	1
2164	1914-01-12	PRINCE RUPERT	BC	1066482	-130.45	54.28	35	4.9	5.3	-0.4	1
2165	1914-01-16	PRINCE RUPERT	BC	1066482	-130.45	54.28	35	0.4	0.6	-0.2	1
2166	1914-01-31	PRINCE RUPERT	BC	1066482	-130.45	54.28	35	0.5	1.2	-0.7	1
2167	1914-02-05	PRINCE RUPERT	BC	1066482	-130.45	54.28	35	0.3	0.6	-0.3	1
2168	1914-03-01	PRINCE RUPERT	BC	1066482	-130.45	54.28	35	3.5	4	-0.5	1
2169	1914-03-02	PRINCE RUPERT	BC	1066482	-130.45	54.28	35	3.5	4	-0.5	1
2170	1914-03-03	PRINCE RUPERT	BC	1066482	-130.45	54.28	35	3	4	-1	1
2171	1914-03-16	PRINCE RUPERT	BC	1066482	-130.45	54.28	35	2.5	4	-1.5	1
2172	1914-04-15	PRINCE RUPERT	BC	1066482	-130.45	54.28	35	3.5	4.7	-1.2	1
2173	1914-04-16	PRINCE RUPERT	BC	1066482	-130.45	54.28	35	2.5	3.9	-1.4	1
2174	1914-04-19	PRINCE RUPERT	BC	1066482	-130.45	54.28	35	4.8	6.6	-1.8	1
2175	1914-04-26	PRINCE RUPERT	BC	1066482	-130.45	54.28	35	4.9	5.2	-0.3	1

2176	1914-05-01	PRINCE RUPERT	BC	1066482	-130.45	54.28	35	4.8	6.5	-1.7	1
2177	1914-07-14	PRINCE RUPERT	BC	1066482	-130.45	54.28	35	12.1	12.7	-0.6	1
2178	1914-07-26	PRINCE RUPERT	BC	1066482	-130.45	54.28	35	9.4	9.7	-0.3	1
2179	1914-08-06	PRINCE RUPERT	BC	1066482	-130.45	54.28	35	11	11.6	-0.6	1
2180	1914-09-06	PRINCE RUPERT	BC	1066482	-130.45	54.28	35	9.4	9.7	-0.3	1
2181	1914-10-17	PRINCE RUPERT	BC	1066482	-130.45	54.28	35	7.6	8.4	-0.8	1
2182	1914-10-19	PRINCE RUPERT	BC	1066482	-130.45	54.28	35	6.3	7.2	-0.9	1
2183	1914-10-31	PRINCE RUPERT	BC	1066482	-130.45	54.28	35	6.3	6.4	-0.1	1
2184	1914-11-01	PRINCE RUPERT	BC	1066482	-130.45	54.28	35	6.3	8	-1.7	1
2185	1914-11-08	PRINCE RUPERT	BC	1066482	-130.45	54.28	35	5.6	6.4	-0.8	1
2186	1914-11-20	PRINCE RUPERT	BC	1066482	-130.45	54.28	35	4.9	6.4	-1.5	1
2187	1914-11-25	PRINCE RUPERT	BC	1066482	-130.45	54.28	35	0.4	0.6	-0.2	1
2188	1914-12-24	PRINCE RUPERT	BC	1066482	-130.45	54.28	35	1.2	2.4	-1.2	1
2189	1914-12-25	PRINCE RUPERT	BC	1066482	-130.45	54.28	35	3.5	3.9	-0.4	1
2190	1914-12-30	PRINCE RUPERT	BC	1066482	-130.45	54.28	35	4.1	4.7	-0.6	1
2191	1915-01-01	PRINCE RUPERT	BC	1066482	-130.45	54.28	35	4.1	5.3	-1.2	1
2192	1915-01-03	PRINCE RUPERT	BC	1066482	-130.45	54.28	35	3.5	3.9	-0.4	1
2193	1915-01-05	PRINCE RUPERT	BC	1066482	-130.45	54.28	35	5.6	5.7	-0.1	1
2194	1915-01-06	PRINCE RUPERT	BC	1066482	-130.45	54.28	35	5.6	6.4	-0.8	1
2195	1915-01-07	PRINCE RUPERT	BC	1066482	-130.45	54.28	35	5.6	8	-2.4	1
2196	1915-01-08	PRINCE RUPERT	BC	1066482	-130.45	54.28	35	3.5	6.4	-2.9	1
2197	1915-01-14	PRINCE RUPERT	BC	1066482	-130.45	54.28	35	0.1	1.2	-1.1	1
2198	1915-02-04	PRINCE RUPERT	BC	1066482	-130.45	54.28	35	1.9	2.2	-0.3	1
2199	1915-06-07	PRINCE RUPERT	BC	1066482	-130.45	54.28	35	7.7	8.7	-1	1
2200	1915-09-03	PRINCE RUPERT	BC	1066482	-130.45	54.28	35	12.6	13.4	-0.8	1
2201	1915-09-29	PRINCE RUPERT	BC	1066482	-130.45	54.28	35	11.2	11.5	-0.3	1
2202	1915-10-08	PRINCE RUPERT	BC	1066482	-130.45	54.28	35	6.3	6.4	-0.1	1
2203	1915-10-17	PRINCE RUPERT	BC	1066482	-130.45	54.28	35	3.5	4.7	-1.2	1
2204	1915-10-28	PRINCE RUPERT	BC	1066482	-130.45	54.28	35	4.9	6.4	-1.5	1
2205	1915-10-29	PRINCE RUPERT	BC	1066482	-130.45	54.28	35	4.9	5.3	-0.4	1
2206	1915-11-05	PRINCE RUPERT	BC	1066482	-130.45	54.28	35	1.2	1.4	-0.2	1
2207	1915-11-12	PRINCE RUPERT	BC	1066482	-130.45	54.28	35	0.3	0.6	-0.3	1
2208	1915-11-19	PRINCE RUPERT	BC	1066482	-130.45	54.28	35	1.9	2.2	-0.3	1
2209	1915-12-05	PRINCE RUPERT	BC	1066482	-130.45	54.28	35	3.5	4	-0.5	1

2210	1915-12-20	PRINCE RUPERT	BC	1066482	-130.45	54.28	35	1.2	2.2	-1	1
2211	1915-12-24	PRINCE RUPERT	BC	1066482	-130.45	54.28	35	0.8	1.4	-0.6	1
2212	1916-02-21	PRINCE RUPERT	BC	1066482	-130.45	54.28	35	1.2	2.2	-1	1
2213	1916-03-12	PRINCE RUPERT	BC	1066482	-130.45	54.28	35	0	1.1	-1.1	1
2214	1916-04-10	PRINCE RUPERT	BC	1066482	-130.45	54.28	35	1.9	3.2	-1.3	1
2215	1916-04-17	PRINCE RUPERT	BC	1066482	-130.45	54.28	35	5.6	6.6	-1	1
2216	1916-05-04	PRINCE RUPERT	BC	1066482	-130.45	54.28	35	2.5	3.3	-0.8	1
2217	1916-05-06	PRINCE RUPERT	BC	1066482	-130.45	54.28	35	0.8	1.2	-0.4	1
2218	1916-05-19	PRINCE RUPERT	BC	1066482	-130.45	54.28	35	6.3	7.2	-0.9	1
2219	1916-10-05	PRINCE RUPERT	BC	1066482	-130.45	54.28	35	9.1	9.7	-0.6	1
2220	1916-10-26	PRINCE RUPERT	BC	1066482	-130.45	54.28	35	6.9	7.9	-1	1
2221	1916-11-01	PRINCE RUPERT	BC	1066482	-130.45	54.28	35	4.1	4.7	-0.6	1
2222	1916-11-08	PRINCE RUPERT	BC	1066482	-130.45	54.28	35	3.5	4.7	-1.2	1
2223	1916-11-20	PRINCE RUPERT	BC	1066482	-130.45	54.28	35	4.1	5.2	-1.1	1
2224	1916-11-24	PRINCE RUPERT	BC	1066482	-130.45	54.28	35	4.1	5.2	-1.1	1
2225	1916-11-25	PRINCE RUPERT	BC	1066482	-130.45	54.28	35	1.9	4	-2.1	1
2226	1916-11-27	PRINCE RUPERT	BC	1066482	-130.45	54.28	35	1.9	2.2	-0.3	1
2227	1916-12-11	PRINCE RUPERT	BC	1066482	-130.45	54.28	35	0.5	0.6	-0.1	1
2228	1916-12-30	PRINCE RUPERT	BC	1066482	-130.45	54.28	35	0.4	0.6	-0.2	1
2229	1916-12-31	PRINCE RUPERT	BC	1066482	-130.45	54.28	35	0.5	0.6	-0.1	1
2230	1917-01-06	PRINCE RUPERT	BC	1066482	-130.45	54.28	35	2.9	4	-1.1	1
2231	1917-01-19	PRINCE RUPERT	BC	1066482	-130.45	54.28	35	1.2	1.5	-0.3	1
2232	1917-01-25	PRINCE RUPERT	BC	1066482	-130.45	54.28	35	1.2	1.6	-0.4	1
2233	1917-01-26	PRINCE RUPERT	BC	1066482	-130.45	54.28	35	0.3	0.6	-0.3	1
2234	1917-02-08	PRINCE RUPERT	BC	1066482	-130.45	54.28	35	4.1	5.3	-1.2	1
2235	1917-02-14	PRINCE RUPERT	BC	1066482	-130.45	54.28	35	5.6	6.4	-0.8	1
2236	1917-02-15	PRINCE RUPERT	BC	1066482	-130.45	54.28	35	7.7	8	-0.3	1
2237	1917-02-16	PRINCE RUPERT	BC	1066482	-130.45	54.28	35	1.2	1.4	-0.2	1
2238	1917-03-18	PRINCE RUPERT	BC	1066482	-130.45	54.28	35	-0.1	0.6	-0.7	1
2239	1917-03-23	PRINCE RUPERT	BC	1066482	-130.45	54.28	35	0.4	0.6	-0.2	1
2240	1917-03-26	PRINCE RUPERT	BC	1066482	-130.45	54.28	35	0.3	0.6	-0.3	1
2241	1917-04-05	PRINCE RUPERT	BC	1066482	-130.45	54.28	35	1.9	2.2	-0.3	1
2242	1917-04-10	PRINCE RUPERT	BC	1066482	-130.45	54.28	35	0.8	1.4	-0.6	1
2243	1917-06-08	PRINCE RUPERT	BC	1066482	-130.45	54.28	35	5	5.2	-0.2	1

2244	1917-08-19	PRINCE RUPERT	BC	1066482	-130.45	54.28	35	13.2	13.4	-0.2	1
2245	1917-10-13	PRINCE RUPERT	BC	1066482	-130.45	54.28	35	7.6	8	-0.4	1
2246	1917-10-15	PRINCE RUPERT	BC	1066482	-130.45	54.28	35	4.1	5.3	-1.2	1
2247	1917-10-24	PRINCE RUPERT	BC	1066482	-130.45	54.28	35	4.1	4.7	-0.6	1
2248	1917-11-27	PRINCE RUPERT	BC	1066482	-130.45	54.28	35	2.5	3	-0.5	1
2249	1917-11-28	PRINCE RUPERT	BC	1066482	-130.45	54.28	35	0.4	0.6	-0.2	1
2250	1917-12-10	PRINCE RUPERT	BC	1066482	-130.45	54.28	35	1.2	1.6	-0.4	1
2251	1918-01-07	PRINCE RUPERT	BC	1066482	-130.45	54.28	35	0.5	0.6	-0.1	1
2252	1918-01-14	PRINCE RUPERT	BC	1066482	-130.45	54.28	35	0.9	1.2	-0.3	1
2253	1918-01-18	PRINCE RUPERT	BC	1066482	-130.45	54.28	35	1.9	2.2	-0.3	1
2254	1918-01-24	PRINCE RUPERT	BC	1066482	-130.45	54.28	35	2.5	3	-0.5	1
2255	1918-01-28	PRINCE RUPERT	BC	1066482	-130.45	54.28	35	0.4	1.6	-1.2	1
2256	1918-01-29	PRINCE RUPERT	BC	1066482	-130.45	54.28	35	0.2	0.6	-0.4	1
2257	1918-02-02	PRINCE RUPERT	BC	1066482	-130.45	54.28	35	0.8	1.2	-0.4	1
2258	1918-02-04	PRINCE RUPERT	BC	1066482	-130.45	54.28	35	3.5	4	-0.5	1
2259	1918-02-10	PRINCE RUPERT	BC	1066482	-130.45	54.28	35	0.8	1.2	-0.4	1
2260	1918-03-01	PRINCE RUPERT	BC	1066482	-130.45	54.28	35	0.3	0.6	-0.3	1
2261	1918-03-02	PRINCE RUPERT	BC	1066482	-130.45	54.28	35	0.5	0.6	-0.1	1
2262	1918-03-18	PRINCE RUPERT	BC	1066482	-130.45	54.28	35	1.2	1.6	-0.4	1
2263	1918-04-20	PRINCE RUPERT	BC	1066482	-130.45	54.28	35	6.3	6.4	-0.1	1
2264	1918-06-18	PRINCE RUPERT	BC	1066482	-130.45	54.28	35	7.6	8.7	-1.1	1
2265	1918-07-29	PRINCE RUPERT	BC	1066482	-130.45	54.28	35	13.2	13.4	-0.2	1
2266	1918-08-23	PRINCE RUPERT	BC	1066482	-130.45	54.28	35	12.6	12.7	-0.1	1
2267	1918-10-20	PRINCE RUPERT	BC	1066482	-130.45	54.28	35	6.4	8	-1.6	1
2268	1918-10-21	PRINCE RUPERT	BC	1066482	-130.45	54.28	35	3.5	5.2	-1.7	1
2269	1918-10-23	PRINCE RUPERT	BC	1066482	-130.45	54.28	35	0.4	1.3	-0.9	1
2270	1918-10-25	PRINCE RUPERT	BC	1066482	-130.45	54.28	35	4.9	5.2	-0.3	1
2271	1918-10-31	PRINCE RUPERT	BC	1066482	-130.45	54.28	35	4.9	5.7	-0.8	1
2272	1918-11-01	PRINCE RUPERT	BC	1066482	-130.45	54.28	35	3.5	4.7	-1.2	1
2273	1918-11-06	PRINCE RUPERT	BC	1066482	-130.45	54.28	35	3.5	4	-0.5	1
2274	1918-11-09	PRINCE RUPERT	BC	1066482	-130.45	54.28	35	1.2	2.4	-1.2	1
2275	1918-11-10	PRINCE RUPERT	BC	1066482	-130.45	54.28	35	0.3	1.1	-0.8	1
2276	1918-11-17	PRINCE RUPERT	BC	1066482	-130.45	54.28	35	0.4	0.6	-0.2	1
2277	1918-11-26	PRINCE RUPERT	BC	1066482	-130.45	54.28	35	0.4	1.3	-0.9	1

2278	1918-11-29	PRINCE RUPERT	BC	1066482	-130.45	54.28	35	1.2	1.4	-0.2	1
2279	1918-12-03	PRINCE RUPERT	BC	1066482	-130.45	54.28	35	0.3	0.6	-0.3	1
2280	1918-12-15	PRINCE RUPERT	BC	1066482	-130.45	54.28	35	1.3	1.4	-0.1	1
2281	1918-12-19	PRINCE RUPERT	BC	1066482	-130.45	54.28	35	1.2	1.6	-0.4	1
2282	1918-12-28	PRINCE RUPERT	BC	1066482	-130.45	54.28	35	0.8	1.4	-0.6	1
2283	1919-01-10	PRINCE RUPERT	BC	1066482	-130.45	54.28	35	3.5	3.9	-0.4	1
2284	1919-01-23	PRINCE RUPERT	BC	1066482	-130.45	54.28	35	-0.1	0.6	-0.7	1
2285	1919-01-30	PRINCE RUPERT	BC	1066482	-130.45	54.28	35	0.4	1	-0.6	1
2286	1919-02-11	PRINCE RUPERT	BC	1066482	-130.45	54.28	35	0.6	1	-0.4	1
2287	1919-02-19	PRINCE RUPERT	BC	1066482	-130.45	54.28	35	1.3	1.4	-0.1	1
2288	1919-03-06	PRINCE RUPERT	BC	1066482	-130.45	54.28	35	0.5	0.6	-0.1	1
2289	1919-03-09	PRINCE RUPERT	BC	1066482	-130.45	54.28	35	0.1	0.6	-0.5	1
2290	1919-03-30	PRINCE RUPERT	BC	1066482	-130.45	54.28	35	8.4	9.1	-0.7	1
2291	1919-03-31	PRINCE RUPERT	BC	1066482	-130.45	54.28	35	6.9	7.1	-0.2	1
2292	1919-04-26	PRINCE RUPERT	BC	1066482	-130.45	54.28	35	6.9	8	-1.1	1
2293	1919-05-08	PRINCE RUPERT	BC	1066482	-130.45	54.28	35	4.8	5.2	-0.4	1
2294	1919-05-22	PRINCE RUPERT	BC	1066482	-130.45	54.28	35	3.5	5.7	-2.2	1
2295	1919-05-23	PRINCE RUPERT	BC	1066482	-130.45	54.28	35	2.5	3.2	-0.7	1
2296	1919-05-25	PRINCE RUPERT	BC	1066482	-130.45	54.28	35	4.1	5.7	-1.6	1
2297	1919-06-02	PRINCE RUPERT	BC	1066482	-130.45	54.28	35	4.8	5.7	-0.9	1
2298	1919-06-26	PRINCE RUPERT	BC	1066482	-130.45	54.28	35	7.7	8.9	-1.2	1
2299	1919-06-27	PRINCE RUPERT	BC	1066482	-130.45	54.28	35	8.4	8.9	-0.5	1
2300	1919-07-27	PRINCE RUPERT	BC	1066482	-130.45	54.28	35	11.1	11.3	-0.2	1
2301	1919-08-18	PRINCE RUPERT	BC	1066482	-130.45	54.28	35	12.2	12.7	-0.5	1
2302	1919-10-21	PRINCE RUPERT	BC	1066482	-130.45	54.28	35	6.4	6.5	-0.1	1
2303	1919-10-27	PRINCE RUPERT	BC	1066482	-130.45	54.28	35	3.5	3.9	-0.4	1
2304	1919-10-31	PRINCE RUPERT	BC	1066482	-130.45	54.28	35	2.5	3.2	-0.7	1
2305	1919-11-02	PRINCE RUPERT	BC	1066482	-130.45	54.28	35	0.6	1	-0.4	1
2306	1919-11-09	PRINCE RUPERT	BC	1066482	-130.45	54.28	35	1.9	2.2	-0.3	1
2307	1919-11-13	PRINCE RUPERT	BC	1066482	-130.45	54.28	35	6.4	6.5	-0.1	1
2308	1919-11-21	PRINCE RUPERT	BC	1066482	-130.45	54.28	35	6.3	6.4	-0.1	1
2309	1919-11-23	PRINCE RUPERT	BC	1066482	-130.45	54.28	35	3.5	3.9	-0.4	1
2310	1919-11-27	PRINCE RUPERT	BC	1066482	-130.45	54.28	35	1.2	1.4	-0.2	1
2311	1919-11-28	PRINCE RUPERT	BC	1066482	-130.45	54.28	35	0.4	1	-0.6	1

2312	1919-11-29	PRINCE RUPERT	BC	1066482	-130.45	54.28	35	0.3	1	-0.7	1
2313	1919-12-15	PRINCE RUPERT	BC	1066482	-130.45	54.28	35	1.3	2.3	-1	1
2314	1919-12-17	PRINCE RUPERT	BC	1066482	-130.45	54.28	35	10.2	10.6	-0.4	1
2315	1919-12-20	PRINCE RUPERT	BC	1066482	-130.45	54.28	35	0.8	2.3	-1.5	1
2316	1919-12-22	PRINCE RUPERT	BC	1066482	-130.45	54.28	35	7.7	8.5	-0.8	1
2317	1919-12-23	PRINCE RUPERT	BC	1066482	-130.45	54.28	35	6.3	6.4	-0.1	1
2318	1919-12-24	PRINCE RUPERT	BC	1066482	-130.45	54.28	35	3.5	4	-0.5	1
2319	1919-12-26	PRINCE RUPERT	BC	1066482	-130.45	54.28	35	6.3	7.2	-0.9	1
2320	1919-12-29	PRINCE RUPERT	BC	1066482	-130.45	54.28	35	0.4	0.6	-0.2	1
2321	1920-01-03	PRINCE RUPERT	BC	1066482	-130.45	54.28	35	2.5	4	-1.5	1
2322	1920-01-07	PRINCE RUPERT	BC	1066482	-130.45	54.28	35	3.5	5.2	-1.7	1
2323	1920-01-11	PRINCE RUPERT	BC	1066482	-130.45	54.28	35	1.2	1.6	-0.4	1
2324	1920-01-30	PRINCE RUPERT	BC	1066482	-130.45	54.28	35	0.8	1.1	-0.3	1
2325	1920-02-17	PRINCE RUPERT	BC	1066482	-130.45	54.28	35	4.2	5.3	-1.1	1
2326	1920-02-18	PRINCE RUPERT	BC	1066482	-130.45	54.28	35	2.5	3.2	-0.7	1
2327	1920-03-07	PRINCE RUPERT	BC	1066482	-130.45	54.28	35	1.2	2.4	-1.2	1
2328	1920-03-10	PRINCE RUPERT	BC	1066482	-130.45	54.28	35	0.3	1.3	-1	1
2329	1920-03-17	PRINCE RUPERT	BC	1066482	-130.45	54.28	35	0	0.1	-0.1	1
2330	1920-03-28	PRINCE RUPERT	BC	1066482	-130.45	54.28	35	1.2	1.3	-0.1	1
2331	1920-04-11	PRINCE RUPERT	BC	1066482	-130.45	54.28	35	7.6	8	-0.4	1
2332	1920-04-16	PRINCE RUPERT	BC	1066482	-130.45	54.28	35	0.5	1.3	-0.8	1
2333	1920-04-18	PRINCE RUPERT	BC	1066482	-130.45	54.28	35	3.5	3.9	-0.4	1
2334	1920-04-28	PRINCE RUPERT	BC	1066482	-130.45	54.28	35	6.3	6.5	-0.2	1
2335	1920-05-03	PRINCE RUPERT	BC	1066482	-130.45	54.28	35	6.3	8	-1.7	1
2336	1920-05-17	PRINCE RUPERT	BC	1066482	-130.45	54.28	35	5	6.6	-1.6	1
2337	1920-05-25	PRINCE RUPERT	BC	1066482	-130.45	54.28	35	7.8	8	-0.2	1
2338	1920-05-30	PRINCE RUPERT	BC	1066482	-130.45	54.28	35	6.3	8	-1.7	1
2339	1920-06-17	PRINCE RUPERT	BC	1066482	-130.45	54.28	35	6.3	7.2	-0.9	1
2340	1920-06-23	PRINCE RUPERT	BC	1066482	-130.45	54.28	35	5.7	6.5	-0.8	1
2341	1920-10-13	PRINCE RUPERT	BC	1066482	-130.45	54.28	35	3.5	3.9	-0.4	1
2342	1920-10-16	PRINCE RUPERT	BC	1066482	-130.45	54.28	35	0.6	1.3	-0.7	1
2343	1920-11-02	PRINCE RUPERT	BC	1066482	-130.45	54.28	35	3.5	5.3	-1.8	1
2344	1920-11-21	PRINCE RUPERT	BC	1066482	-130.45	54.28	35	2.5	3.9	-1.4	1
2345	1920-11-22	PRINCE RUPERT	BC	1066482	-130.45	54.28	35	3	5.3	-2.3	1

2346	1920-11-29	PRINCE RUPERT	BC	1066482	-130.45	54.28	35	2.5	3.8	-1.3	1
2347	1920-11-30	PRINCE RUPERT	BC	1066482	-130.45	54.28	35	0.4	0.6	-0.2	1
2348	1920-12-02	PRINCE RUPERT	BC	1066482	-130.45	54.28	35	0.5	0.6	-0.1	1
2349	1920-12-04	PRINCE RUPERT	BC	1066482	-130.45	54.28	35	0	1.1	-1.1	1
2350	1920-12-06	PRINCE RUPERT	BC	1066482	-130.45	54.28	35	3	4.7	-1.7	1
2351	1920-12-08	PRINCE RUPERT	BC	1066482	-130.45	54.28	35	0	0.6	-0.6	1
2352	1920-12-09	PRINCE RUPERT	BC	1066482	-130.45	54.28	35	-0.2	0.2	-0.4	1
2353	1920-12-11	PRINCE RUPERT	BC	1066482	-130.45	54.28	35	0.1	0.6	-0.5	1
2354	1920-12-12	PRINCE RUPERT	BC	1066482	-130.45	54.28	35	-0.1	0.6	-0.7	1
2355	1920-12-15	PRINCE RUPERT	BC	1066482	-130.45	54.28	35	-0.1	0.6	-0.7	1
2356	1920-12-24	PRINCE RUPERT	BC	1066482	-130.45	54.28	35	1.3	1.4	-0.1	1
2357	1920-12-26	PRINCE RUPERT	BC	1066482	-130.45	54.28	35	0.5	1.5	-1	1
2358	1920-12-31	PRINCE RUPERT	BC	1066482	-130.45	54.28	35	0.3	0.6	-0.3	1
2359	1921-01-01	PRINCE RUPERT	BC	1066482	-130.45	54.28	35	1.2	1.5	-0.3	1
2360	1921-01-03	PRINCE RUPERT	BC	1066482	-130.45	54.28	35	1.2	1.5	-0.3	1
2361	1921-01-22	PRINCE RUPERT	BC	1066482	-130.45	54.28	35	0.4	0.6	-0.2	1
2362	1921-01-23	PRINCE RUPERT	BC	1066482	-130.45	54.28	35	0.2	0.6	-0.4	1
2363	1921-01-24	PRINCE RUPERT	BC	1066482	-130.45	54.28	35	1.2	1.5	-0.3	1
2364	1921-02-06	PRINCE RUPERT	BC	1066482	-130.45	54.28	35	0.4	0.6	-0.2	1
2365	1921-02-11	PRINCE RUPERT	BC	1066482	-130.45	54.28	35	0.5	1	-0.5	1
2366	1921-02-25	PRINCE RUPERT	BC	1066482	-130.45	54.28	35	5.1	6.4	-1.3	1
2367	1921-02-27	PRINCE RUPERT	BC	1066482	-130.45	54.28	35	5	5.7	-0.7	1
2368	1921-02-28	PRINCE RUPERT	BC	1066482	-130.45	54.28	35	1.2	2.2	-1	1
2369	1921-03-24	PRINCE RUPERT	BC	1066482	-130.45	54.28	35	0.2	0.6	-0.4	1
2370	1921-04-01	PRINCE RUPERT	BC	1066482	-130.45	54.28	35	1.3	2.1	-0.8	1
2371	1921-04-11	PRINCE RUPERT	BC	1066482	-130.45	54.28	35	3.5	5.2	-1.7	1
2372	1921-04-20	PRINCE RUPERT	BC	1066482	-130.45	54.28	35	3.5	4.1	-0.6	1
2373	1921-05-06	PRINCE RUPERT	BC	1066482	-130.45	54.28	35	2.5	4.1	-1.6	1
2374	1921-05-19	PRINCE RUPERT	BC	1066482	-130.45	54.28	35	4.9	5.2	-0.3	1
2375	1921-08-07	PRINCE RUPERT	BC	1066482	-130.45	54.28	35	14.4	14.5	-0.1	1
2376	1921-10-23	PRINCE RUPERT	BC	1066482	-130.45	54.28	35	5	5.3	-0.3	1
2377	1926-10-18	PRINCE RUPERT	BC	1066482	-130.45	54.28	35	8.6	8.8	-0.2	1
2378	1926-10-19	PRINCE RUPERT	BC	1066482	-130.45	54.28	35	8.6	8.8	-0.2	1
2379	1926-10-26	PRINCE RUPERT	BC	1066482	-130.45	54.28	35	7.8	8.4	-0.6	1

2380	1926-11-12	PRINCE RUPERT	BC	1066482	-130.45	54.28	35	8.6	9.1	-0.5	1
2381	1926-11-14	PRINCE RUPERT	BC	1066482	-130.45	54.28	35	8.6	9.1	-0.5	1
2382	1926-11-16	PRINCE RUPERT	BC	1066482	-130.45	54.28	35	5.8	6.4	-0.6	1
2383	1926-12-05	PRINCE RUPERT	BC	1066482	-130.45	54.28	35	7.2	8	-0.8	1
2384	1926-12-06	PRINCE RUPERT	BC	1066482	-130.45	54.28	35	7.2	8	-0.8	1
2385	1926-12-07	PRINCE RUPERT	BC	1066482	-130.45	54.28	35	5.8	8	-2.2	1
2386	1927-04-24	PRINCE RUPERT	BC	1066482	-130.45	54.28	35	5.1	5.3	-0.2	1
2387	1927-10-06	PRINCE RUPERT	BC	1066482	-130.45	54.28	35	7.8	8	-0.2	1
2388	1928-01-05	PRINCE RUPERT	BC	1066482	-130.45	54.28	35	5.1	5.2	-0.1	1
2389	1928-05-04	PRINCE RUPERT	BC	1066482	-130.45	54.28	35	5.2	5.3	-0.1	1
2390	1928-11-11	PRINCE RUPERT	BC	1066482	-130.45	54.28	35	4.7	5.2	-0.5	1
2391	1930-02-18	PRINCE RUPERT	BC	1066482	-130.45	54.28	35	4.6	5.3	-0.7	1
2392	1930-10-23	PRINCE RUPERT	BC	1066482	-130.45	54.28	35	8.5	9.1	-0.6	1
2393	1930-11-22	PRINCE RUPERT	BC	1066482	-130.45	54.28	35	5.8	6.3	-0.5	1
2394	1930-12-01	PRINCE RUPERT	BC	1066482	-130.45	54.28	35	5.8	6.3	-0.5	1
2395	1930-12-06	PRINCE RUPERT	BC	1066482	-130.45	54.28	35	7.8	7.9	-0.1	1
2396	1931-05-26	PRINCE RUPERT	BC	1066482	-130.45	54.28	35	4.7	5.2	-0.5	1
2397	1932-02-23	PRINCE RUPERT	BC	1066482	-130.45	54.28	35	5.1	5.7	-0.6	1
2398	1932-02-24	PRINCE RUPERT	BC	1066482	-130.45	54.28	35	5.1	5.3	-0.2	1
2399	1932-02-26	PRINCE RUPERT	BC	1066482	-130.45	54.28	35	5.8	6.4	-0.6	1
2400	1933-08-05	PRINCE RUPERT	BC	1066482	-130.45	54.28	35	13.7	13.9	-0.2	1
2401	1935-01-30	PRINCE RUPERT	BC	1066482	-130.45	54.28	35	6.4	6.5	-0.1	1
2402	1935-10-19	PRINCE RUPERT	BC	1066482	-130.45	54.28	35	4.8	5.3	-0.5	1
2403	1938-10-29	PRINCE RUPERT	BC	1066482	-130.45	54.28	35	8.5	8.8	-0.3	1
2404	1939-03-30	PRINCE RUPERT	BC	1066482	-130.45	54.28	35	5.8	6.4	-0.6	1
2405	1939-03-31	PRINCE RUPERT	BC	1066482	-130.45	54.28	35	4.8	5.3	-0.5	1
2406	1939-05-07	PRINCE RUPERT	BC	1066482	-130.45	54.28	35	5.8	7.2	-1.4	1
2407	1941-05-14	PRINCE RUPERT	BC	1066482	-130.45	54.28	35	6.4	6.5	-0.1	1
2408	1941-10-24	PRINCE RUPERT	BC	1066482	-130.45	54.28	35	8.6	8.8	-0.2	1
2409	1942-06-10	PRINCE RUPERT	BC	1066482	-130.45	54.28	35	8.5	8.7	-0.2	1
2410	1943-09-03	PRINCE RUPERT	BC	1066482	-130.45	54.28	35	10.7	11.4	-0.7	1
2411	1944-05-31	PRINCE RUPERT	BC	1066482	-130.45	54.28	35	7.1	7.3	-0.2	1
2412	1944-12-04	PRINCE RUPERT	BC	1066482	-130.45	54.28	35	6.3	6.4	-0.1	1
2413	1946-11-05	PRINCE RUPERT	BC	1066482	-130.45	54.28	35	5.1	5.3	-0.2	1

2414	1946-12-20	PRINCE RUPERT	BC	1066482	-130.45	54.28	35	4.6	4.7	-0.1	1
2415	1947-01-22	PRINCE RUPERT	BC	1066482	-130.45	54.28	35	5.1	5.7	-0.6	1
2416	1948-01-21	PRINCE RUPERT	BC	1066482	-130.45	54.28	35	4.8	5.2	-0.4	1
2417	1950-12-24	PRINCE RUPERT	BC	1066482	-130.45	54.28	35	5.1	5.3	-0.2	1
2418	1954-11-25	PRINCE RUPERT	BC	1066482	-130.45	54.28	35	6.4	7.2	-0.8	1
2419	1954-11-28	PRINCE RUPERT	BC	1066482	-130.45	54.28	35	4.4	4.7	-0.3	1
2420	1955-06-29	PRINCE RUPERT	BC	1066482	-130.45	54.28	35	7.8	8.4	-0.6	1
2421	1957-12-08	PRINCE RUPERT	BC	1066482	-130.45	54.28	35	5.1	5.3	-0.2	1
2422	1958-09-06	PRINCE RUPERT	BC	1066482	-130.45	54.28	35	13.3	13.4	-0.1	1
2423	1958-12-15	PRINCE RUPERT	BC	1066482	-130.45	54.28	35	6.5	7.3	-0.8	1
2424	1958-12-18	PRINCE RUPERT	BC	1066482	-130.45	54.28	35	5.1	5.7	-0.6	1
2425	1959-11-08	PRINCE RUPERT	BC	1066482	-130.45	54.28	35	7.8	8	-0.2	1
2426	1959-11-20	PRINCE RUPERT	BC	1066482	-130.45	54.28	35	5.1	5.3	-0.2	1
2427	1960-03-18	PRINCE RUPERT	BC	1066482	-130.45	54.28	35	5.1	5.7	-0.6	1
2428	1960-11-01	PRINCE RUPERT	BC	1066482	-130.45	54.28	35	6.3	6.4	-0.1	1
2429	1960-12-01	PRINCE RUPERT	BC	1066482	-130.45	54.28	35	4.3	4.7	-0.4	1
2430	2008-10-28	VAVENBY	BC	1168520	-119.78	51.58	445	-8	-6	-2	1
2431	2014-12-25	VAVENBY	BC	1168520	-119.78	51.58	445	-2.5	-0.5	-2	1
2432	1947-02-09	SAINT JOHN	NB	8104901	-65.88	45.32	109	-5	-4.4	-0.6	1
2433	1947-06-09	SAINT JOHN	NB	8104901	-65.88	45.32	109	7.8	9	-1.2	1
2434	1947-11-14	SAINT JOHN	NB	8104901	-65.88	45.32	109	2.8	2.9	-0.1	1
2435	1947-11-19	SAINT JOHN	NB	8104901	-65.88	45.32	109	2.8	2.9	-0.1	1
2436	1948-10-25	SAINT JOHN	NB	8104901	-65.88	45.32	109	9.4	9.6	-0.2	1
2437	1948-11-21	SAINT JOHN	NB	8104901	-65.88	45.32	109	3.3	3.5	-0.2	1
2438	1949-01-04	SAINT JOHN	NB	8104901	-65.88	45.32	109	-1.1	-0.6	-0.5	1
2439	1949-03-12	SAINT JOHN	NB	8104901	-65.88	45.32	109	0.6	0.7	-0.1	1
2440	1988-07-15	SABLE ISLAND	NS	8204700	-60.02	43.93	5	12.8	13.7	-0.9	1
2441	1898-01-20	FORT ST JAMES	BC	1092970	-124.25	54.45	691	-3.3	-3	-0.3	1
2442	1898-01-28	FORT ST JAMES	BC	1092970	-124.25	54.45	691	-3.3	-3	-0.3	1
2443	1898-02-06	FORT ST JAMES	BC	1092970	-124.25	54.45	691	-12.2	-11.7	-0.5	1
2444	1993-01-25	FORT ST JAMES	BC	1092970	-124.25	54.45	691	-7	-5.5	-1.5	1
2445	2009-12-09	FORT ST JAMES	BC	1092970	-124.25	54.45	691	-11	-8.5	-2.5	1
2446	2009-12-28	PINAWA	MAN	5032162	-96.07	50.18	267	-19	-15	-4	1
2447	2010-01-17	PINAWA	MAN	5032162	-96.07	50.18	267	-4	-2	-2	1

2448	2010-03-24	PINAWA	MAN	5032162	-96.07	50.18	267	-10.5	-7	-3.5	1
2449	2014-02-03	PINAWA	MAN	5032162	-96.07	50.18	267	-18	-16.5	-1.5	1
2450	2015-01-28	PINAWA	MAN	5032162	-96.07	50.18	267	-9	-7.5	-1.5	1
2451	2016-11-15	PINAWA	MAN	5032162	-96.07	50.18	267	1	2	-1	1
2452	2016-12-08	PINAWA	MAN	5032162	-96.07	50.18	267	-10	-9	-1	1
2453	2006-11-28	EXPLOITS DAM	NFLD	8401550	-56.6	48.77	154	0	2	-2	1
2454	2008-11-28	EXPLOITS DAM	NFLD	8401550	-56.6	48.77	154	3	5	-2	1
2455	2006-12-27	KELOWNA	BC	1123993	-119.48	49.87	417	-2	-1	-1	1
2456	2010-09-25	BAKER LAKE	NU	2300503	-96.08	64.3	19	-0.1	1.5	-1.6	1
2457	2017-12-28	BAKER LAKE	NU	2300503	-96.08	64.3	19	-32.8	-29.6	-3.2	1
2458	2019-10-16	BAKER LAKE	NU	2300503	-96.08	64.3	19	-5.3	-0.1	-5.2	1
2459	2019-10-17	BAKER LAKE	NU	2300503	-96.08	64.3	19	-0.1	0	-0.1	1
2460	2018-11-14	VAL D'OR	QUE	7098603	-77.78	48.05	339	-10.8	-9.2	-1.6	1
2461	2018-11-22	VAL D'OR	QUE	7098603	-77.78	48.05	339	-12.3	-8.6	-3.7	1
2462	2018-11-23	VAL D'OR	QUE	7098603	-77.78	48.05	339	-2.6	-0.8	-1.8	1
2463	1926-03-04	COLD LAKE	ALTA	3081680	-110.28	54.42	541	-10.1	-9.9	-0.2	1
2464	1926-12-02	COLD LAKE	ALTA	3081680	-110.28	54.42	541	-17.2	-16.3	-0.9	1
2465	1929-02-01	COLD LAKE	ALTA	3081680	-110.28	54.42	541	-22.1	-22	-0.1	1
2466	1930-01-04	COLD LAKE	ALTA	3081680	-110.28	54.42	541	-22.1	-21.9	-0.2	1
2467	1930-06-02	COLD LAKE	ALTA	3081680	-110.28	54.42	541	8.9	9.2	-0.3	1
2468	1930-06-12	COLD LAKE	ALTA	3081680	-110.28	54.42	541	10.6	11.6	-1	1
2469	1932-10-15	COLD LAKE	ALTA	3081680	-110.28	54.42	541	-5.3	-4.9	-0.4	1
2470	1934-01-26	COLD LAKE	ALTA	3081680	-110.28	54.42	541	6.2	6.3	-0.1	1
2471	1934-12-24	COLD LAKE	ALTA	3081680	-110.28	54.42	541	-29.8	-28.5	-1.3	1
2472	1937-12-28	COLD LAKE	ALTA	3081680	-110.28	54.42	541	-24.3	-23.1	-1.2	1
2473	1938-10-31	COLD LAKE	ALTA	3081680	-110.28	54.42	541	1.6	2	-0.4	1
2474	1940-11-07	COLD LAKE	ALTA	3081680	-110.28	54.42	541	-16.6	-16.3	-0.3	1
2475	1940-12-30	COLD LAKE	ALTA	3081680	-110.28	54.42	541	-14.5	-14.3	-0.2	1
2476	1941-12-30	COLD LAKE	ALTA	3081680	-110.28	54.42	541	-19.8	-17.8	-2	1
2477	1942-03-21	COLD LAKE	ALTA	3081680	-110.28	54.42	541	10.1	11.1	-1	1
2478	1944-05-10	COLD LAKE	ALTA	3081680	-110.28	54.42	541	1.6	2	-0.4	1
2479	1944-06-01	COLD LAKE	ALTA	3081680	-110.28	54.42	541	12.1	12.2	-0.1	1
2480	1945-03-26	COLD LAKE	ALTA	3081680	-110.28	54.42	541	5.6	5.7	-0.1	1
2481	1945-09-20	COLD LAKE	ALTA	3081680	-110.28	54.42	541	4.4	5.7	-1.3	1

2482	1947-01-05	COLD LAKE	ALTA	3081680	-110.28	54.42	541	-6.7	-6.4	-0.3	1
2483	1947-04-02	COLD LAKE	ALTA	3081680	-110.28	54.42	541	0.6	0.7	-0.1	1
2484	1948-12-11	COLD LAKE	ALTA	3081680	-110.28	54.42	541	-24.4	-23.7	-0.7	1
2485	1949-01-25	COLD LAKE	ALTA	3081680	-110.28	54.42	541	-21.7	-20.3	-1.4	1
2486	1949-02-23	COLD LAKE	ALTA	3081680	-110.28	54.42	541	-17.8	-17.3	-0.5	1
2487	1951-07-14	COLD LAKE	ALTA	3081680	-110.28	54.42	541	11.1	12.1	-1	1
2488	1952-12-08	COLD LAKE	ALTA	3081680	-110.28	54.42	541	-6.1	-5.9	-0.2	1
2489	1914-09-24	SIOUX LOOKOUT	ONT	6037776	-91.9	50.12	383	9.3	9.9	-0.6	1
2490	1917-09-26	SIOUX LOOKOUT	ONT	6037776	-91.9	50.12	383	10.2	11	-0.8	1
2491	1919-09-15	SIOUX LOOKOUT	ONT	6037776	-91.9	50.12	383	9.7	11.6	-1.9	1
2492	1919-10-07	SIOUX LOOKOUT	ONT	6037776	-91.9	50.12	383	7.9	8.8	-0.9	1
2493	1979-11-11	CHARLOTTETOWN	PEI	8300301	-63.13	46.28	49	3.6	3.7	-0.1	1
2494	1994-02-18	SCHEFFERVILLE	QUE	7117827	-66.82	54.8	517	-22.8	-19.1	-3.7	1
2495	1994-11-15	SCHEFFERVILLE	QUE	7117827	-66.82	54.8	517	-2.4	1	-3.4	1
2496	2012-12-15	SCHEFFERVILLE	QUE	7117827	-66.82	54.8	517	-21.6	-19.5	-2.1	1
2497	2012-12-16	SCHEFFERVILLE	QUE	7117827	-66.82	54.8	517	-16.6	-16.3	-0.3	1
2498	2012-12-18	SCHEFFERVILLE	QUE	7117827	-66.82	54.8	517	-12	-11.6	-0.4	1
2499	2012-12-21	SCHEFFERVILLE	QUE	7117827	-66.82	54.8	517	-11.3	-7.7	-3.6	1
2500	2013-03-14	SCHEFFERVILLE	QUE	7117827	-66.82	54.8	517	-12.1	-8.4	-3.7	1
2501	2013-03-16	SCHEFFERVILLE	QUE	7117827	-66.82	54.8	517	-20.9	-20.5	-0.4	1
2502	2013-03-27	SCHEFFERVILLE	QUE	7117827	-66.82	54.8	517	-8.1	-7.7	-0.4	1
2503	1978-11-26	KEY LAKE	SASK	4063755	-107.1	57.4	509	-24.4	-22.7	-1.7	1
2504	1991-11-13	KEY LAKE	SASK	4063755	-107.1	57.4	509	-9	-7.2	-1.8	1
2505	1991-11-17	KEY LAKE	SASK	4063755	-107.1	57.4	509	-12.5	-11.8	-0.7	1
2506	1991-11-18	KEY LAKE	SASK	4063755	-107.1	57.4	509	-17	-15.6	-1.4	1
2507	1991-11-28	KEY LAKE	SASK	4063755	-107.1	57.4	509	-19	-7.2	-11.8	1
2508	1950-11-07	CORNWALL	ONT	6101874	-74.75	45.02	64	9.8	10.2	-0.4	1
2509	1951-01-28	CORNWALL	ONT	6101874	-74.75	45.02	64	-15	-14.9	-0.1	1
2510	1952-12-01	CORNWALL	ONT	6101874	-74.75	45.02	64	0.6	1.3	-0.7	1
2511	1953-11-01	CORNWALL	ONT	6101874	-74.75	45.02	64	4.8	5.3	-0.5	1
2512	1953-12-05	CORNWALL	ONT	6101874	-74.75	45.02	64	6.9	7	-0.1	1
2513	1953-12-12	CORNWALL	ONT	6101874	-74.75	45.02	64	6.4	6.5	-0.1	1
2514	1955-04-25	CORNWALL	ONT	6101874	-74.75	45.02	64	6.9	7.5	-0.6	1
2515	2007-03-05	CORNWALL	ONT	6101874	-74.75	45.02	64	-7.5	-6	-1.5	1

2516	2007-03-14	CORNWALL	ONT	6101874	-74.75	45.02	64	10.5	11	-0.5	1
2517	1903-11-17	GOLDEN	BC	1173210	-116.98	51.3	785	-13	-11.2	-1.8	1
2518	1906-12-28	GOLDEN	BC	1173210	-116.98	51.3	785	-11.7	-11.2	-0.5	1
2519	1907-01-31	GOLDEN	BC	1173210	-116.98	51.3	785	-13.7	-12.5	-1.2	1
2520	1908-12-22	GOLDEN	BC	1173210	-116.98	51.3	785	-13	-12.5	-0.5	1
2521	1909-12-02	GOLDEN	BC	1173210	-116.98	51.3	785	-11	-9.5	-1.5	1
2522	1909-12-19	GOLDEN	BC	1173210	-116.98	51.3	785	-7.9	-7.3	-0.6	1
2523	1909-12-20	GOLDEN	BC	1173210	-116.98	51.3	785	-16.1	-16	-0.1	1
2524	1910-12-31	GOLDEN	BC	1173210	-116.98	51.3	785	-11	-8.3	-2.7	1
2525	1911-01-25	GOLDEN	BC	1173210	-116.98	51.3	785	-13	-11.3	-1.7	1
2526	1911-01-31	GOLDEN	BC	1173210	-116.98	51.3	785	-12.4	-11.3	-1.1	1
2527	1911-02-01	GOLDEN	BC	1173210	-116.98	51.3	785	-19	-17.5	-1.5	1
2528	1911-11-08	GOLDEN	BC	1173210	-116.98	51.3	785	-11	-9.5	-1.5	1
2529	1912-12-11	GOLDEN	BC	1173210	-116.98	51.3	785	-9.6	-9.5	-0.1	1
2530	1913-03-17	GOLDEN	BC	1173210	-116.98	51.3	785	-11	-8.3	-2.7	1
2531	1914-02-04	GOLDEN	BC	1173210	-116.98	51.3	785	-14.3	-13.9	-0.4	1
2532	1916-01-10	GOLDEN	BC	1173210	-116.98	51.3	785	-22.9	-22.5	-0.4	1
2533	1916-01-23	GOLDEN	BC	1173210	-116.98	51.3	785	-19	-16.8	-2.2	1
2534	1921-01-12	GOLDEN	BC	1173210	-116.98	51.3	785	-13	-12.5	-0.5	1
2535	1921-01-16	GOLDEN	BC	1173210	-116.98	51.3	785	-14.3	-11.2	-3.1	1
2536	1921-01-24	GOLDEN	BC	1173210	-116.98	51.3	785	-8.9	-7.9	-1	1
2537	1922-12-18	GOLDEN	BC	1173210	-116.98	51.3	785	-19.5	-18.1	-1.4	1
2538	1922-12-19	GOLDEN	BC	1173210	-116.98	51.3	785	-12.3	-10	-2.3	1
2539	1924-01-21	GOLDEN	BC	1173210	-116.98	51.3	785	-11.7	-10.6	-1.1	1
2540	1926-01-12	GOLDEN	BC	1173210	-116.98	51.3	785	-8	-6.9	-1.1	1
2541	1927-01-14	GOLDEN	BC	1173210	-116.98	51.3	785	-14.3	-13.2	-1.1	1
2542	1927-01-15	GOLDEN	BC	1173210	-116.98	51.3	785	-7.9	-7.4	-0.5	1
2543	1927-01-23	GOLDEN	BC	1173210	-116.98	51.3	785	-14.9	-14.5	-0.4	1
2544	1932-12-01	GOLDEN	BC	1173210	-116.98	51.3	785	3.9	4.1	-0.2	1
2545	1933-10-24	GOLDEN	BC	1173210	-116.98	51.3	785	2.8	2.9	-0.1	1
2546	1933-12-11	GOLDEN	BC	1173210	-116.98	51.3	785	-13.1	-11.3	-1.8	1
2547	1933-12-13	GOLDEN	BC	1173210	-116.98	51.3	785	-14.4	-13.9	-0.5	1
2548	1934-11-18	GOLDEN	BC	1173210	-116.98	51.3	785	3.9	4	-0.1	1
2549	1934-12-13	GOLDEN	BC	1173210	-116.98	51.3	785	4.5	4.7	-0.2	1

2550	1934-12-24	GOLDEN	BC	1173210	-116.98	51.3	785	-15.5	-14.6	-0.9	1
2551	1935-11-11	GOLDEN	BC	1173210	-116.98	51.3	785	-7.7	-6.8	-0.9	1
2552	1935-12-25	GOLDEN	BC	1173210	-116.98	51.3	785	-3.3	-3.1	-0.2	1
2553	1936-01-17	GOLDEN	BC	1173210	-116.98	51.3	785	-3.3	-2.8	-0.5	1
2554	1936-12-31	GOLDEN	BC	1173210	-116.98	51.3	785	-15.5	-15.4	-0.1	1
2555	1938-01-06	GOLDEN	BC	1173210	-116.98	51.3	785	-7.1	-6.8	-0.3	1
2556	1938-02-11	GOLDEN	BC	1173210	-116.98	51.3	785	-7.7	-6.8	-0.9	1
2557	1938-02-14	GOLDEN	BC	1173210	-116.98	51.3	785	-13.2	-12.5	-0.7	1
2558	1938-12-23	GOLDEN	BC	1173210	-116.98	51.3	785	-14.3	-11.3	-3	1
2559	1938-12-27	GOLDEN	BC	1173210	-116.98	51.3	785	-20.1	-19.4	-0.7	1
2560	1939-11-04	GOLDEN	BC	1173210	-116.98	51.3	785	3.9	4.1	-0.2	1
2561	1939-11-06	GOLDEN	BC	1173210	-116.98	51.3	785	2.8	2.9	-0.1	1
2562	1939-12-11	GOLDEN	BC	1173210	-116.98	51.3	785	2.8	3.5	-0.7	1
2563	1940-01-07	GOLDEN	BC	1173210	-116.98	51.3	785	-6.4	-5.6	-0.8	1
2564	1940-02-05	GOLDEN	BC	1173210	-116.98	51.3	785	-7.7	-6.8	-0.9	1
2565	1940-11-24	GOLDEN	BC	1173210	-116.98	51.3	785	-4.8	-4.4	-0.4	1
2566	1940-11-26	GOLDEN	BC	1173210	-116.98	51.3	785	-3.3	-2.7	-0.6	1
2567	1942-01-08	GOLDEN	BC	1173210	-116.98	51.3	785	-36.7	-36.6	-0.1	1
2568	1942-01-13	GOLDEN	BC	1173210	-116.98	51.3	785	-4.7	-4.4	-0.3	1
2569	1942-11-15	GOLDEN	BC	1173210	-116.98	51.3	785	3.9	4.7	-0.8	1
2570	1942-12-24	GOLDEN	BC	1173210	-116.98	51.3	785	-10.6	-10.1	-0.5	1
2571	1943-01-11	GOLDEN	BC	1173210	-116.98	51.3	785	-6.3	-5.6	-0.7	1
2572	1943-03-29	GOLDEN	BC	1173210	-116.98	51.3	785	4.5	4.7	-0.2	1
2573	1943-11-12	GOLDEN	BC	1173210	-116.98	51.3	785	-4	-3.4	-0.6	1
2574	1943-11-22	GOLDEN	BC	1173210	-116.98	51.3	785	-6.4	-5.6	-0.8	1
2575	1943-12-07	GOLDEN	BC	1173210	-116.98	51.3	785	-4.8	-4.4	-0.4	1
2576	1943-12-13	GOLDEN	BC	1173210	-116.98	51.3	785	-9.4	-8.4	-1	1
2577	1943-12-14	GOLDEN	BC	1173210	-116.98	51.3	785	-10.6	-10.1	-0.5	1
2578	1944-01-13	GOLDEN	BC	1173210	-116.98	51.3	785	-9.2	-8.4	-0.8	1
2579	1944-11-27	GOLDEN	BC	1173210	-116.98	51.3	785	2.4	2.9	-0.5	1
2580	1944-12-11	GOLDEN	BC	1173210	-116.98	51.3	785	-10.6	-10.1	-0.5	1
2581	1944-12-31	GOLDEN	BC	1173210	-116.98	51.3	785	-11.9	-10.7	-1.2	1
2582	1945-11-12	GOLDEN	BC	1173210	-116.98	51.3	785	1.5	1.6	-0.1	1
2583	1945-12-14	GOLDEN	BC	1173210	-116.98	51.3	785	-11.9	-10.7	-1.2	1

2584	1945-12-20	GOLDEN	BC	1173210	-116.98	51.3	785	-12.5	-12	-0.5	1
2585	1946-02-02	GOLDEN	BC	1173210	-116.98	51.3	785	-6.5	-6.2	-0.3	1
2586	1946-11-18	GOLDEN	BC	1173210	-116.98	51.3	785	-14.3	-13.3	-1	1
2587	1946-11-19	GOLDEN	BC	1173210	-116.98	51.3	785	-16.1	-15.3	-0.8	1
2588	1947-01-13	GOLDEN	BC	1173210	-116.98	51.3	785	-12.6	-10.7	-1.9	1
2589	1948-01-13	GOLDEN	BC	1173210	-116.98	51.3	785	-12.6	-11.9	-0.7	1
2590	1948-12-13	GOLDEN	BC	1173210	-116.98	51.3	785	-13.2	-12.6	-0.6	1
2591	1949-02-10	GOLDEN	BC	1173210	-116.98	51.3	785	-7.8	-6.8	-1	1
2592	1950-01-12	GOLDEN	BC	1173210	-116.98	51.3	785	-21.7	-21.5	-0.2	1
2593	1950-01-22	GOLDEN	BC	1173210	-116.98	51.3	785	-13.2	-12.6	-0.6	1
2594	1951-01-03	GOLDEN	BC	1173210	-116.98	51.3	785	-9.4	-9	-0.4	1
2595	1951-01-17	GOLDEN	BC	1173210	-116.98	51.3	785	-4.1	-3.4	-0.7	1
2596	1951-01-25	GOLDEN	BC	1173210	-116.98	51.3	785	-4.7	-3.9	-0.8	1
2597	1951-01-26	GOLDEN	BC	1173210	-116.98	51.3	785	-15	-14.6	-0.4	1
2598	1951-12-09	GOLDEN	BC	1173210	-116.98	51.3	785	-11.9	-10.1	-1.8	1
2599	1952-01-14	GOLDEN	BC	1173210	-116.98	51.3	785	-13.8	-12.5	-1.3	1
2600	1952-12-02	GOLDEN	BC	1173210	-116.98	51.3	785	-8.5	-8.4	-0.1	1
2601	1956-12-30	GOLDEN	BC	1173210	-116.98	51.3	785	-6.3	-5.6	-0.7	1
2602	1957-01-02	GOLDEN	BC	1173210	-116.98	51.3	785	-3.4	-3.1	-0.3	1
2603	1957-02-23	GOLDEN	BC	1173210	-116.98	51.3	785	-18.4	-18	-0.4	1
2604	1996-11-27	KAMLOOPS	BC	1163781	-120.45	50.7	345	-1.6	0.2	-1.8	1
2605	1999-12-06	KAMLOOPS	BC	1163781	-120.45	50.7	345	3	3.6	-0.6	1
2606	2019-12-22	FORT SMITH	NWT	2202201	-111.97	60.02	205	-16.7	-15.9	-0.8	1
2607	2019-12-23	FORT SMITH	NWT	2202201	-111.97	60.02	205	-13.5	-12.3	-1.2	1
2608	1996-05-31	FLIN FLON	MAN	5050920	-101.88	54.77	320	5.5	11.5	-6	1
2609	1993-12-09	WOODSTOCK	ONT	6149625	-80.77	43.13	282	-7	0	-7	1
2610	1993-12-10	WOODSTOCK	ONT	6149625	-80.77	43.13	282	0.5	4.5	-4	1
2611	1993-12-20	WOODSTOCK	ONT	6149625	-80.77	43.13	282	-2	0	-2	1
2612	1993-12-21	WOODSTOCK	ONT	6149625	-80.77	43.13	282	-5.5	-0.5	-5	1
2613	1999-11-10	WOODSTOCK	ONT	6149625	-80.77	43.13	282	7	10.5	-3.5	1
2614	1999-11-13	WOODSTOCK	ONT	6149625	-80.77	43.13	282	4	5	-1	1
2615	1999-11-14	WOODSTOCK	ONT	6149625	-80.77	43.13	282	0.5	5.5	-5	1
2616	1999-11-24	WOODSTOCK	ONT	6149625	-80.77	43.13	282	7	7.5	-0.5	1
2617	1999-11-28	WOODSTOCK	ONT	6149625	-80.77	43.13	282	-2.5	0	-2.5	1

2618	2007-01-15	WOODSTOCK	ONT	6149625	-80.77	43.13	282	-3	-2.5	-0.5	1
2619	2008-11-16	WOODSTOCK	ONT	6149625	-80.77	43.13	282	-2	-0.5	-1.5	1
2620	2012-11-23	WOODSTOCK	ONT	6149625	-80.77	43.13	282	4	9	-5	1
2621	2013-04-19	WOODSTOCK	ONT	6149625	-80.77	43.13	282	-0.5	13	-13.5	1
2622	2013-12-24	WOODSTOCK	ONT	6149625	-80.77	43.13	282	-5	-1.5	-3.5	1
2623	2014-12-28	WOODSTOCK	ONT	6149625	-80.77	43.13	282	-3.5	1	-4.5	1
2624	2015-12-24	WOODSTOCK	ONT	6149625	-80.77	43.13	282	9.5	11	-1.5	1
2625	2017-03-09	WOODSTOCK	ONT	6149625	-80.77	43.13	282	-4	-2	-2	1
2626	1980-03-11	BEAUCEVILLE	QUE	7027283	-70.7	46.15	168	-9	-5	-4	1
2627	1984-08-01	BEAUCEVILLE	QUE	7027283	-70.7	46.15	168	17	20	-3	1
2628	2013-05-13	ILES MADELEINE	QUE	7053250	-61.78	47.42	11	8.5	9.4	-0.9	1
2629	2013-05-17	ILES MADELEINE	QUE	7053250	-61.78	47.42	11	3.8	5.4	-1.6	1
2630	2013-05-24	ILES MADELEINE	QUE	7053250	-61.78	47.42	11	8.3	8.8	-0.5	1
2631	2016-02-17	ILES MADELEINE	QUE	7053250	-61.78	47.42	11	-0.3	2.4	-2.7	1
2632	2016-02-18	ILES MADELEINE	QUE	7053250	-61.78	47.42	11	-3.1	-2.7	-0.4	1
2633	2016-02-21	ILES MADELEINE	QUE	7053250	-61.78	47.42	11	-4.3	-1.3	-3	1
2634	2016-02-22	ILES MADELEINE	QUE	7053250	-61.78	47.42	11	-6.5	-6.3	-0.2	1
2635	2016-02-26	ILES MADELEINE	QUE	7053250	-61.78	47.42	11	-4.6	1.8	-6.4	1
2636	1937-11-16	OUTLOOK	SASK	4055736	-107.05	51.48	541	-9.5	-9.4	-0.1	1
2637	1939-12-21	OUTLOOK	SASK	4055736	-107.05	51.48	541	-9.5	-9.4	-0.1	1
2638	1940-03-19	OUTLOOK	SASK	4055736	-107.05	51.48	541	-7.9	-7.8	-0.1	1
2639	2009-01-22	OUTLOOK	SASK	4055736	-107.05	51.48	541	-25.2	-16.7	-8.5	1
2640	2002-10-31	CORNER BROOK	NFLD	8401300	-57.95	48.95	5	0	2	-2	1
2641	2004-09-30	CORNER BROOK	NFLD	8401300	-57.95	48.95	5	0	2.5	-2.5	1
2642	1993-11-19	DEASE LAKE	BC	1192341	-130	58.42	803	-19.1	-7	-12.1	1
2643	1993-11-20	DEASE LAKE	BC	1192341	-130	58.42	803	-15.9	-9.8	-6.1	1
2644	1993-11-25	DEASE LAKE	BC	1192341	-130	58.42	803	-2.7	-2.4	-0.3	1
2645	1993-12-11	DEASE LAKE	BC	1192341	-130	58.42	803	-18	-11.5	-6.5	1
2646	1993-12-25	DEASE LAKE	BC	1192341	-130	58.42	803	-9.9	-4.4	-5.5	1
2647	2008-03-14	PELLY RANCH	YT	2100880	-137.37	62.82	445	-5.5	-2.4	-3.1	1
2648	2013-02-16	PELLY RANCH	YT	2100880	-137.37	62.82	445	-6	-2	-4	1
2649	1893-05-15	HALIBURTON	ONT	6163171	-78.53	45.03	330	8.7	8.9	-0.2	1
2650	1894-03-23	HALIBURTON	ONT	6163171	-78.53	45.03	330	-2	-1.7	-0.3	1
2651	1894-12-27	HALIBURTON	ONT	6163171	-78.53	45.03	330	-20.1	-20	-0.1	1

2652	1895-01-13	HALIBURTON	ONT	6163171	-78.53	45.03	330	-13.4	-13.3	-0.1	1
2653	1895-11-19	HALIBURTON	ONT	6163171	-78.53	45.03	330	-8.9	-2.2	-6.7	1
2654	1895-11-20	HALIBURTON	ONT	6163171	-78.53	45.03	330	-13.4	-10	-3.4	1
2655	1899-10-28	HALIBURTON	ONT	6163171	-78.53	45.03	330	3.6	3.9	-0.3	1
2656	1899-11-10	HALIBURTON	ONT	6163171	-78.53	45.03	330	-1.6	0	-1.6	1
2657	1899-11-19	HALIBURTON	ONT	6163171	-78.53	45.03	330	2.7	5	-2.3	1
2658	1899-11-25	HALIBURTON	ONT	6163171	-78.53	45.03	330	-4	-1.1	-2.9	1
2659	1900-09-16	HALIBURTON	ONT	6163171	-78.53	45.03	330	10.3	12.8	-2.5	1
2660	1901-01-10	HALIBURTON	ONT	6163171	-78.53	45.03	330	-11.2	-11.1	-0.1	1
2661	1901-01-16	HALIBURTON	ONT	6163171	-78.53	45.03	330	-3.5	-2.2	-1.3	1
2662	1901-01-17	HALIBURTON	ONT	6163171	-78.53	45.03	330	-19	-6.7	-12.3	1
2663	1901-01-21	HALIBURTON	ONT	6163171	-78.53	45.03	330	-10	-9.4	-0.6	1
2664	1901-01-24	HALIBURTON	ONT	6163171	-78.53	45.03	330	-5.7	-5	-0.7	1
2665	1901-01-28	HALIBURTON	ONT	6163171	-78.53	45.03	330	-10.6	-10	-0.6	1
2666	1906-11-10	HALIBURTON	ONT	6163171	-78.53	45.03	330	-1	0	-1	1
2667	1911-12-24	HALIBURTON	ONT	6163171	-78.53	45.03	330	-0.3	0	-0.3	1
2668	1917-07-11	HALIBURTON	ONT	6163171	-78.53	45.03	330	14.5	15	-0.5	1
2669	1919-03-04	HALIBURTON	ONT	6163171	-78.53	45.03	330	1	1.1	-0.1	1
2670	1922-12-06	HALIBURTON	ONT	6163171	-78.53	45.03	330	-5.8	-5.6	-0.2	1
2671	1923-11-06	HALIBURTON	ONT	6163171	-78.53	45.03	330	2.6	3.3	-0.7	1
2672	1928-01-13	HALIBURTON	ONT	6163171	-78.53	45.03	330	1	1.1	-0.1	1
2673	1928-01-25	HALIBURTON	ONT	6163171	-78.53	45.03	330	-12.3	-12.2	-0.1	1
2674	1930-03-11	HALIBURTON	ONT	6163171	-78.53	45.03	330	0.3	0.6	-0.3	1
2675	1930-12-14	HALIBURTON	ONT	6163171	-78.53	45.03	330	-12.3	-11.1	-1.2	1
2676	1931-02-01	HALIBURTON	ONT	6163171	-78.53	45.03	330	-10.6	-9.4	-1.2	1
2677	1932-03-26	HALIBURTON	ONT	6163171	-78.53	45.03	330	4.2	4.4	-0.2	1
2678	1932-04-01	HALIBURTON	ONT	6163171	-78.53	45.03	330	0.3	0.6	-0.3	1
2679	1932-04-12	HALIBURTON	ONT	6163171	-78.53	45.03	330	2.7	3.3	-0.6	1
2680	1932-04-13	HALIBURTON	ONT	6163171	-78.53	45.03	330	-2	-1.7	-0.3	1
2681	1932-04-26	HALIBURTON	ONT	6163171	-78.53	45.03	330	4.8	5.6	-0.8	1
2682	1988-01-25	HALIBURTON	ONT	6163171	-78.53	45.03	330	-10	-6	-4	1
2683	1987-01-18	IROQUOIS FALLS	ONT	6073810	-80.67	48.75	259	-26	-24	-2	1
2684	1995-10-28	IROQUOIS FALLS	ONT	6073810	-80.67	48.75	259	-1	1	-2	1
2685	2006-11-22	KENORA	ONT	6034076	-94.37	49.78	410	-1.5	2.2	-3.7	1

2686	2011-11-10	KENORA	ONT	6034076	-94.37	49.78	410	-2.4	-2.2	-0.2	1
2687	1991-01-18	PRINCETON	BC	1126510	-120.52	49.47	702	-5	-0.5	-4.5	1
2688	1914-11-06	TERRACE	BC	1068134	-128.58	54.47	217	5.4	5.6	-0.2	1
2689	1916-05-04	TERRACE	BC	1068134	-128.58	54.47	217	8.6	8.9	-0.3	1
2690	1918-04-19	TERRACE	BC	1068134	-128.58	54.47	217	4.2	4.4	-0.2	1
2691	1920-12-21	TERRACE	BC	1068134	-128.58	54.47	217	-3	-2.8	-0.2	1
2692	1920-12-28	TERRACE	BC	1068134	-128.58	54.47	217	0.4	0.6	-0.2	1
2693	1930-11-22	TERRACE	BC	1068134	-128.58	54.47	217	7.1	7.2	-0.1	1
2694	1939-11-28	TERRACE	BC	1068134	-128.58	54.47	217	4.8	5	-0.2	1
2695	1943-11-21	TERRACE	BC	1068134	-128.58	54.47	217	4.9	5	-0.1	1
2696	1944-10-29	TERRACE	BC	1068134	-128.58	54.47	217	9.9	10	-0.1	1
2697	1949-11-01	TERRACE	BC	1068134	-128.58	54.47	217	7.1	7.2	-0.1	1
2698	1951-01-25	TERRACE	BC	1068134	-128.58	54.47	217	-5.4	-2.2	-3.2	1
2699	1951-01-26	TERRACE	BC	1068134	-128.58	54.47	217	-12.7	-7.8	-4.9	1
2700	1952-09-16	TERRACE	BC	1068134	-128.58	54.47	217	9.3	9.4	-0.1	1
2701	1952-11-27	TERRACE	BC	1068134	-128.58	54.47	217	-0.7	-0.6	-0.1	1
2702	1952-11-28	TERRACE	BC	1068134	-128.58	54.47	217	-0.7	0	-0.7	1
2703	1991-10-11	TERRACE	BC	1068134	-128.58	54.47	217	12.4	13.8	-1.4	1
2704	1938-01-15	WHITESAND DAM	SASK	4067655	-103.15	56.23	344	-21.9	-21.1	-0.8	1
2705	1938-02-28	WHITESAND DAM	SASK	4067655	-103.15	56.23	344	-6.1	-5.6	-0.5	1
2706	1938-04-22	WHITESAND DAM	SASK	4067655	-103.15	56.23	344	-12.6	-12.2	-0.4	1
2707	1938-05-21	WHITESAND DAM	SASK	4067655	-103.15	56.23	344	3.7	4.4	-0.7	1
2708	1938-05-28	WHITESAND DAM	SASK	4067655	-103.15	56.23	344	6.2	6.7	-0.5	1
2709	1939-01-20	WHITESAND DAM	SASK	4067655	-103.15	56.23	344	-17	-16.7	-0.3	1
2710	1942-10-20	WHITESAND DAM	SASK	4067655	-103.15	56.23	344	-1.7	-1.1	-0.6	1
2711	1942-10-23	WHITESAND DAM	SASK	4067655	-103.15	56.23	344	-7.2	-6.7	-0.5	1
2712	1943-08-09	WHITESAND DAM	SASK	4067655	-103.15	56.23	344	12.4	12.8	-0.4	1
2713	1951-12-29	WHITESAND DAM	SASK	4067655	-103.15	56.23	344	-27.1	-21.1	-6	1
2714	1952-11-16	WHITESAND DAM	SASK	4067655	-103.15	56.23	344	-0.8	-0.6	-0.2	1
2715	1952-11-17	WHITESAND DAM	SASK	4067655	-103.15	56.23	344	-1.3	-1.1	-0.2	1
2716	1953-10-28	WHITESAND DAM	SASK	4067655	-103.15	56.23	344	-2.8	-2.2	-0.6	1
2717	1953-11-07	WHITESAND DAM	SASK	4067655	-103.15	56.23	344	-2.3	-2.2	-0.1	1
2718	1954-08-22	WHITESAND DAM	SASK	4067655	-103.15	56.23	344	14	14.4	-0.4	1
2719	1956-10-25	WHITESAND DAM	SASK	4067655	-103.15	56.23	344	-4.9	-1.1	-3.8	1

2720	1957-03-20	WHITESAND DAM	SASK	4067655	-103.15	56.23	344	-4.4	-3.3	-1.1	1
2721	1957-10-20	WHITESAND DAM	SASK	4067655	-103.15	56.23	344	-5.9	0	-5.9	1
2722	1957-10-30	WHITESAND DAM	SASK	4067655	-103.15	56.23	344	-1.1	0	-1.1	1
2723	1958-03-15	WHITESAND DAM	SASK	4067655	-103.15	56.23	344	-12.2	-11.1	-1.1	1
2724	1964-12-11	WHITESAND DAM	SASK	4067655	-103.15	56.23	344	-17.5	-17.2	-0.3	1
2725	1964-12-12	WHITESAND DAM	SASK	4067655	-103.15	56.23	344	-21.2	-21.1	-0.1	1
2726	1964-12-13	WHITESAND DAM	SASK	4067655	-103.15	56.23	344	-23.6	-23.3	-0.3	1
2727	1965-02-20	WHITESAND DAM	SASK	4067655	-103.15	56.23	344	-26.1	-25.6	-0.5	1
2728	1964-09-22	NORMANDIN	QUE	7065639	-72.53	48.85	137	16.1	21.7	-5.6	1
2729	1893-09-28	HAY RIVER	NWT	2202401	-115.78	60.83	165	4.7	4.8	-0.1	1
2730	1894-01-12	HAY RIVER	NWT	2202401	-115.78	60.83	165	-39.1	-38.7	-0.4	1
2731	1894-01-13	HAY RIVER	NWT	2202401	-115.78	60.83	165	-38.5	-37.7	-0.8	1
2732	1894-04-13	HAY RIVER	NWT	2202401	-115.78	60.83	165	-16.7	-16.3	-0.4	1
2733	1894-06-08	HAY RIVER	NWT	2202401	-115.78	60.83	165	2.4	3.2	-0.8	1
2734	1894-06-11	HAY RIVER	NWT	2202401	-115.78	60.83	165	1.7	2.2	-0.5	1
2735	1894-06-26	HAY RIVER	NWT	2202401	-115.78	60.83	165	6.4	6.8	-0.4	1
2736	1894-06-28	HAY RIVER	NWT	2202401	-115.78	60.83	165	3.3	4.9	-1.6	1
2737	1894-11-08	HAY RIVER	NWT	2202401	-115.78	60.83	165	-15.4	-15.2	-0.2	1
2738	1894-11-14	HAY RIVER	NWT	2202401	-115.78	60.83	165	-12	-11.1	-0.9	1
2739	1894-11-16	HAY RIVER	NWT	2202401	-115.78	60.83	165	-22.2	-21.7	-0.5	1
2740	1894-12-05	HAY RIVER	NWT	2202401	-115.78	60.83	165	-21.6	-21	-0.6	1
2741	1895-01-04	HAY RIVER	NWT	2202401	-115.78	60.83	165	-21.7	-21	-0.7	1
2742	1895-01-06	HAY RIVER	NWT	2202401	-115.78	60.83	165	-44.6	-40.3	-4.3	1
2743	1895-01-13	HAY RIVER	NWT	2202401	-115.78	60.83	165	-27.2	-21.1	-6.1	1
2744	1895-04-14	HAY RIVER	NWT	2202401	-115.78	60.83	165	9.2	9.4	-0.2	1
2745	1895-05-05	HAY RIVER	NWT	2202401	-115.78	60.83	165	1.3	1.5	-0.2	1
2746	1895-06-25	HAY RIVER	NWT	2202401	-115.78	60.83	165	11.4	18.6	-7.2	1
2747	1895-07-01	HAY RIVER	NWT	2202401	-115.78	60.83	165	8.8	10.1	-1.3	1
2748	1895-09-01	HAY RIVER	NWT	2202401	-115.78	60.83	165	11.6	13.1	-1.5	1
2749	1895-09-05	HAY RIVER	NWT	2202401	-115.78	60.83	165	3.8	5.4	-1.6	1
2750	1895-09-17	HAY RIVER	NWT	2202401	-115.78	60.83	165	2.1	2.2	-0.1	1
2751	1895-10-05	HAY RIVER	NWT	2202401	-115.78	60.83	165	2.3	4	-1.7	1
2752	1895-10-25	HAY RIVER	NWT	2202401	-115.78	60.83	165	0.6	1.5	-0.9	1
2753	1895-11-02	HAY RIVER	NWT	2202401	-115.78	60.83	165	-7.1	-6.6	-0.5	1

2754	1895-11-12	HAY RIVER	NWT	2202401	-115.78	60.83	165	-14	-13.5	-0.5	1
2755	1895-11-15	HAY RIVER	NWT	2202401	-115.78	60.83	165	-14	-12.3	-1.7	1
2756	1895-11-16	HAY RIVER	NWT	2202401	-115.78	60.83	165	-19.2	-18.6	-0.6	1
2757	1895-11-21	HAY RIVER	NWT	2202401	-115.78	60.83	165	-19.2	-18.1	-1.1	1
2758	1895-11-24	HAY RIVER	NWT	2202401	-115.78	60.83	165	-20.3	-19.8	-0.5	1
2759	1895-12-23	HAY RIVER	NWT	2202401	-115.78	60.83	165	-29.2	-27.1	-2.1	1
2760	1895-12-26	HAY RIVER	NWT	2202401	-115.78	60.83	165	-25.4	-25.3	-0.1	1
2761	1896-01-01	HAY RIVER	NWT	2202401	-115.78	60.83	165	-33.5	-32.5	-1	1
2762	1896-01-12	HAY RIVER	NWT	2202401	-115.78	60.83	165	-36.3	-35.7	-0.6	1
2763	1896-01-23	HAY RIVER	NWT	2202401	-115.78	60.83	165	-37.4	-37.2	-0.2	1
2764	1896-02-16	HAY RIVER	NWT	2202401	-115.78	60.83	165	-27.6	-26.5	-1.1	1
2765	1896-02-17	HAY RIVER	NWT	2202401	-115.78	60.83	165	-25.8	-18.1	-7.7	1
2766	1896-02-18	HAY RIVER	NWT	2202401	-115.78	60.83	165	-4.9	-2.8	-2.1	1
2767	1896-02-21	HAY RIVER	NWT	2202401	-115.78	60.83	165	-12.6	-9.8	-2.8	1
2768	1896-03-12	HAY RIVER	NWT	2202401	-115.78	60.83	165	-12	-5.3	-6.7	1
2769	1896-05-14	HAY RIVER	NWT	2202401	-115.78	60.83	165	1.3	1.5	-0.2	1
2770	1896-09-03	HAY RIVER	NWT	2202401	-115.78	60.83	165	6.8	7.4	-0.6	1
2771	1896-09-21	HAY RIVER	NWT	2202401	-115.78	60.83	165	3.8	4	-0.2	1
2772	1896-09-27	HAY RIVER	NWT	2202401	-115.78	60.83	165	4.7	5.8	-1.1	1
2773	1896-11-05	HAY RIVER	NWT	2202401	-115.78	60.83	165	-4.9	-4.8	-0.1	1
2774	1896-11-07	HAY RIVER	NWT	2202401	-115.78	60.83	165	-9	-7.9	-1.1	1
2775	1896-11-08	HAY RIVER	NWT	2202401	-115.78	60.83	165	-11.2	-11.1	-0.1	1
2776	1896-11-09	HAY RIVER	NWT	2202401	-115.78	60.83	165	-15.4	-15.2	-0.2	1
2777	1897-10-02	HAY RIVER	NWT	2202401	-115.78	60.83	165	0.9	1	-0.1	1
2778	1897-11-06	HAY RIVER	NWT	2202401	-115.78	60.83	165	-8.4	-7.3	-1.1	1
2779	1897-12-28	HAY RIVER	NWT	2202401	-115.78	60.83	165	-20.7	-20.4	-0.3	1
2780	1897-12-29	HAY RIVER	NWT	2202401	-115.78	60.83	165	-16.6	-16.3	-0.3	1
2781	1898-01-22	HAY RIVER	NWT	2202401	-115.78	60.83	165	-21.3	-19.8	-1.5	1
2782	1898-07-02	HAY RIVER	NWT	2202401	-115.78	60.83	165	11.3	13.6	-2.3	1
2783	1898-08-27	HAY RIVER	NWT	2202401	-115.78	60.83	165	9.9	11.3	-1.4	1
2784	1898-08-28	HAY RIVER	NWT	2202401	-115.78	60.83	165	7.3	9.3	-2	1
2785	1898-09-20	HAY RIVER	NWT	2202401	-115.78	60.83	165	8.9	9.3	-0.4	1
2786	1898-11-16	HAY RIVER	NWT	2202401	-115.78	60.83	165	-21.3	-21.1	-0.2	1
2787	1898-12-11	HAY RIVER	NWT	2202401	-115.78	60.83	165	-18	-17.5	-0.5	1

2788	1898-12-15	HAY RIVER	NWT	2202401	-115.78	60.83	165	-15.4	-15.2	-0.2	1
2789	1899-01-24	HAY RIVER	NWT	2202401	-115.78	60.83	165	-20.7	-19.2	-1.5	1
2790	1899-04-21	HAY RIVER	NWT	2202401	-115.78	60.83	165	2.1	2.6	-0.5	1
2791	1899-05-08	HAY RIVER	NWT	2202401	-115.78	60.83	165	3.3	4.4	-1.1	1
2792	1899-07-11	HAY RIVER	NWT	2202401	-115.78	60.83	165	12	13.1	-1.1	1
2793	1899-07-15	HAY RIVER	NWT	2202401	-115.78	60.83	165	11.6	11.9	-0.3	1
2794	1899-08-08	HAY RIVER	NWT	2202401	-115.78	60.83	165	10.2	11.3	-1.1	1
2795	1899-08-09	HAY RIVER	NWT	2202401	-115.78	60.83	165	9.2	10	-0.8	1
2796	1899-09-30	HAY RIVER	NWT	2202401	-115.78	60.83	165	5.8	6.3	-0.5	1
2797	1899-10-01	HAY RIVER	NWT	2202401	-115.78	60.83	165	0.2	1.5	-1.3	1
2798	1899-11-01	HAY RIVER	NWT	2202401	-115.78	60.83	165	0.5	1	-0.5	1
2799	1899-11-30	HAY RIVER	NWT	2202401	-115.78	60.83	165	-16.6	-16.3	-0.3	1
2800	1899-12-01	HAY RIVER	NWT	2202401	-115.78	60.83	165	-19.7	-19.2	-0.5	1
2801	1900-01-05	HAY RIVER	NWT	2202401	-115.78	60.83	165	-21.3	-21.1	-0.2	1
2802	1900-07-09	HAY RIVER	NWT	2202401	-115.78	60.83	165	11.5	13.1	-1.6	1
2803	1900-08-02	HAY RIVER	NWT	2202401	-115.78	60.83	165	11.6	13.6	-2	1
2804	1900-10-21	HAY RIVER	NWT	2202401	-115.78	60.83	165	1.3	1.6	-0.3	1
2805	1900-12-06	HAY RIVER	NWT	2202401	-115.78	60.83	165	-21.3	-19.2	-2.1	1
2806	1900-12-19	HAY RIVER	NWT	2202401	-115.78	60.83	165	-17.4	-15.2	-2.2	1
2807	1901-10-05	HAY RIVER	NWT	2202401	-115.78	60.83	165	3.3	3.6	-0.3	1
2808	1902-10-07	HAY RIVER	NWT	2202401	-115.78	60.83	165	4.3	4.8	-0.5	1
2809	1903-08-12	HAY RIVER	NWT	2202401	-115.78	60.83	165	24.9	26.4	-1.5	1
2810	1903-10-22	HAY RIVER	NWT	2202401	-115.78	60.83	165	-0.5	5.8	-6.3	1
2811	1903-11-12	HAY RIVER	NWT	2202401	-115.78	60.83	165	-18	-16.9	-1.1	1
2812	1903-12-15	HAY RIVER	NWT	2202401	-115.78	60.83	165	-20.3	-19.2	-1.1	1
2813	1903-12-17	HAY RIVER	NWT	2202401	-115.78	60.83	165	-20.3	-18.1	-2.2	1
2814	1903-12-26	HAY RIVER	NWT	2202401	-115.78	60.83	165	-20.3	-19.8	-0.5	1
2815	1903-12-29	HAY RIVER	NWT	2202401	-115.78	60.83	165	-21.7	-21.1	-0.6	1
2816	1904-01-08	HAY RIVER	NWT	2202401	-115.78	60.83	165	-21.7	-20.4	-1.3	1
2817	1904-01-16	HAY RIVER	NWT	2202401	-115.78	60.83	165	-37.4	-37.1	-0.3	1
2818	1904-08-25	HAY RIVER	NWT	2202401	-115.78	60.83	165	10.9	11.3	-0.4	1
2819	1904-11-11	HAY RIVER	NWT	2202401	-115.78	60.83	165	0	0.3	-0.3	1
2820	1904-11-21	HAY RIVER	NWT	2202401	-115.78	60.83	165	-15.4	-15.2	-0.2	1
2821	1904-11-24	HAY RIVER	NWT	2202401	-115.78	60.83	165	-16.7	-16.3	-0.4	1

2822	1904-11-27	HAY RIVER	NWT	2202401	-115.78	60.83	165	-16	-15.8	-0.2	1
2823	1904-11-28	HAY RIVER	NWT	2202401	-115.78	60.83	165	-19.7	-18.1	-1.6	1
2824	1905-04-07	HAY RIVER	NWT	2202401	-115.78	60.83	165	-3.8	-3.3	-0.5	1
2825	1905-08-15	HAY RIVER	NWT	2202401	-115.78	60.83	165	12.4	13.6	-1.2	1
2826	1905-08-16	HAY RIVER	NWT	2202401	-115.78	60.83	165	11.2	11.9	-0.7	1
2827	1905-08-17	HAY RIVER	NWT	2202401	-115.78	60.83	165	9.9	10.8	-0.9	1
2828	1905-08-28	HAY RIVER	NWT	2202401	-115.78	60.83	165	10.2	10.7	-0.5	1
2829	1905-09-08	HAY RIVER	NWT	2202401	-115.78	60.83	165	0.9	2.2	-1.3	1
2830	1905-12-06	HAY RIVER	NWT	2202401	-115.78	60.83	165	-23	-22.9	-0.1	1
2831	1905-12-15	HAY RIVER	NWT	2202401	-115.78	60.83	165	-19.2	-18.1	-1.1	1
2832	1906-01-04	HAY RIVER	NWT	2202401	-115.78	60.83	165	-22.7	-21.1	-1.6	1
2833	1906-01-19	HAY RIVER	NWT	2202401	-115.78	60.83	165	-35.8	-35.3	-0.5	1
2834	1907-07-10	HAY RIVER	NWT	2202401	-115.78	60.83	165	2.8	4.1	-1.3	1
2835	1907-10-01	HAY RIVER	NWT	2202401	-115.78	60.83	165	2.3	3.6	-1.3	1
2836	1907-10-29	HAY RIVER	NWT	2202401	-115.78	60.83	165	0.3	1.5	-1.2	1
2837	1908-03-05	HAY RIVER	NWT	2202401	-115.78	60.83	165	-12	-11.1	-0.9	1
2838	1925-08-14	BANFF	ALTA	3050519	-115.55	51.2	1397	9.5	9.7	-0.2	1
2839	1993-11-18	CHURCHILL FALLS	NFLD	8501131	-64.1	53.55	440	-7.1	-3.4	-3.7	1
2840	1993-11-24	CHURCHILL FALLS	NFLD	8501131	-64.1	53.55	440	-9.4	-1.3	-8.1	1
2841	1996-01-16	CHURCHILL FALLS	NFLD	8501131	-64.1	53.55	440	-29.1	-27.4	-1.7	1
2842	1996-01-17	CHURCHILL FALLS	NFLD	8501131	-64.1	53.55	440	-18.9	-12.4	-6.5	1
2843	1996-01-26	CHURCHILL FALLS	NFLD	8501131	-64.1	53.55	440	-26.6	-25	-1.6	1
2844	2002-10-28	CHURCHILL FALLS	NFLD	8501131	-64.1	53.55	440	-3	-2.9	-0.1	1
2845	2015-11-11	CHURCHILL FALLS	NFLD	8501131	-64.1	53.55	440	-6.6	-6.5	-0.1	1
2846	1978-01-27	MINE CENTRE	ONT	6025205	-92.6	48.8	361	-14.4	-6	-8.4	1
2847	2007-09-24	MINE CENTRE	ONT	6025205	-92.6	48.8	361	15	17	-2	1
2848	2007-11-21	MINE CENTRE	ONT	6025205	-92.6	48.8	361	-7	-6	-1	1
2849	2007-11-26	MINE CENTRE	ONT	6025205	-92.6	48.8	361	-7	0	-7	1
2850	2007-12-03	MINE CENTRE	ONT	6025205	-92.6	48.8	361	-11.5	-10	-1.5	1
2851	2013-05-21	MINE CENTRE	ONT	6025205	-92.6	48.8	361	9	10	-1	1
2852	2014-09-29	MINE CENTRE	ONT	6025205	-92.6	48.8	361	7.5	12	-4.5	1
2853	1936-03-24	CAMERON FALLS	ONT	6041110	-88.35	49.15	233	5.1	5.2	-0.1	1
2854	1953-05-29	CAMERON FALLS	ONT	6041110	-88.35	49.15	233	6.7	6.9	-0.2	1
2855	1962-10-13	CAMERON FALLS	ONT	6041110	-88.35	49.15	233	9.4	9.5	-0.1	1

2856	1962-10-25	CAMERON FALLS	ONT	6041110	-88.35	49.15	233	-3.3	-1.3	-2	1
2857	1962-10-28	CAMERON FALLS	ONT	6041110	-88.35	49.15	233	1.7	2.2	-0.5	1
2858	1963-12-20	CAMERON FALLS	ONT	6041110	-88.35	49.15	233	-16.7	-15.7	-1	1
2859	1966-01-21	CAMERON FALLS	ONT	6041110	-88.35	49.15	233	-12.8	-12.6	-0.2	1
2860	1966-12-08	CAMERON FALLS	ONT	6041110	-88.35	49.15	233	-6.7	-6.3	-0.4	1
2861	1968-02-28	CAMERON FALLS	ONT	6041110	-88.35	49.15	233	-12.2	-12.1	-0.1	1
2862	1973-01-04	CAMERON FALLS	ONT	6041110	-88.35	49.15	233	-15	-13.5	-1.5	1
2863	1981-11-17	CAMERON FALLS	ONT	6041110	-88.35	49.15	233	5	5.3	-0.3	1
2864	1992-10-28	CAMERON FALLS	ONT	6041110	-88.35	49.15	233	-0.5	0.5	-1	1
2865	1994-01-12	CAMERON FALLS	ONT	6041110	-88.35	49.15	233	-25	-22.2	-2.8	1
2866	1994-01-17	CAMERON FALLS	ONT	6041110	-88.35	49.15	233	-30	-28.4	-1.6	1
2867	1994-01-28	CAMERON FALLS	ONT	6041110	-88.35	49.15	233	-20	-17.3	-2.7	1
2868	1995-05-16	CAMERON FALLS	ONT	6041110	-88.35	49.15	233	6	6.7	-0.7	1
2869	1997-02-24	CAMERON FALLS	ONT	6041110	-88.35	49.15	233	-11	-10.5	-0.5	1
2870	2008-12-15	OLDS	ALTA	3024925	-114.1	51.78	1046	-22	-18.2	-3.8	1
2871	2008-12-26	OLDS	ALTA	3024925	-114.1	51.78	1046	-15	-8.8	-6.2	1
2872	2009-12-13	BELLA COOLA	BC	1060841	-126.68	52.37	36	-9.5	-6.4	-3.1	1
2873	1996-11-28	MAYO	YT	2100701	-135.87	63.62	504	-31.2	-10	-21.2	1
2874	2006-10-04	MAYO	YT	2100701	-135.87	63.62	504	0.5	3.7	-3.2	1
2875	2018-12-15	MAYO	YT	2100701	-135.87	63.62	504	-19.4	-3.9	-15.5	1
2876	2018-12-24	MAYO	YT	2100701	-135.87	63.62	504	-29.9	-21.9	-8	1
2877	2018-12-25	MAYO	YT	2100701	-135.87	63.62	504	-24.8	-17.9	-6.9	1
2878	2018-12-26	MAYO	YT	2100701	-135.87	63.62	504	-18.7	-16.4	-2.3	1
2879	1990-02-06	BIG TROUT LAKE	ONT	6010735	-89.87	53.83	223	-2.3	18.1	-20.4	1
2880	1993-07-18	BIG TROUT LAKE	ONT	6010735	-89.87	53.83	223	11.9	12.7	-0.8	1
2881	1993-10-25	BIG TROUT LAKE	ONT	6010735	-89.87	53.83	223	-5.3	-2.6	-2.7	1
2882	1962-01-22	CAMROSE	ALTA	3011240	-112.82	53.03	739	-5.6	-1	-4.6	1
2883	1958-12-20	PELLY BAY	NU	2303092	-89.8	68.53	16	-24.9	-24.1	-0.8	1
2884	1959-03-12	PELLY BAY	NU	2303092	-89.8	68.53	16	-36.7	-36.6	-0.1	1
2885	1959-05-12	PELLY BAY	NU	2303092	-89.8	68.53	16	-12.4	-10.2	-2.2	1
2886	1959-05-15	PELLY BAY	NU	2303092	-89.8	68.53	16	-10.2	-9.7	-0.5	1
2887	1960-01-19	PELLY BAY	NU	2303092	-89.8	68.53	16	-19.8	-18.1	-1.7	1
2888	1960-11-19	PELLY BAY	NU	2303092	-89.8	68.53	16	-30.1	-27.4	-2.7	1
2889	1960-11-25	PELLY BAY	NU	2303092	-89.8	68.53	16	-15.6	-13.6	-2	1

2890	1960-12-13	PELLY BAY	NU	2303092	-89.8	68.53	16	-18.6	-18.1	-0.5	1
2891	1965-03-16	PELLY BAY	NU	2303092	-89.8	68.53	16	-38	-37.9	-0.1	1
2892	1966-01-01	PELLY BAY	NU	2303092	-89.8	68.53	16	-38	-37.9	-0.1	1
2893	1982-03-28	PELLY BAY	NU	2303092	-89.8	68.53	16	-31.6	-28.2	-3.4	1
2894	1984-04-17	PELLY BAY	NU	2303092	-89.8	68.53	16	-11.5	-6.8	-4.7	1
2895	2007-10-05	PELLY BAY	NU	2303092	-89.8	68.53	16	-6.4	-4.9	-1.5	1
2896	2007-10-10	PELLY BAY	NU	2303092	-89.8	68.53	16	-2.8	-1.8	-1	1
2897	2007-12-18	PELLY BAY	NU	2303092	-89.8	68.53	16	-30.9	-30.1	-0.8	1
2898	2008-01-02	PELLY BAY	NU	2303092	-89.8	68.53	16	-33.9	-33.6	-0.3	1
2899	2008-01-20	PELLY BAY	NU	2303092	-89.8	68.53	16	-33.6	-31.4	-2.2	1
2900	2008-01-25	PELLY BAY	NU	2303092	-89.8	68.53	16	-33.6	-33.1	-0.5	1
2901	2008-01-26	PELLY BAY	NU	2303092	-89.8	68.53	16	-36.8	-35.6	-1.2	1
2902	2008-02-07	PELLY BAY	NU	2303092	-89.8	68.53	16	-39.9	-36.5	-3.4	1
2903	2009-03-31	PELLY BAY	NU	2303092	-89.8	68.53	16	-20.1	-17.5	-2.6	1
2904	2011-10-23	PELLY BAY	NU	2303092	-89.8	68.53	16	-12	-11.5	-0.5	1
2905	2012-04-11	PELLY BAY	NU	2303092	-89.8	68.53	16	-20.5	-20	-0.5	1
2906	1914-07-17	DEMING	NS	8201410	-61.18	45.22	16	15.4	15.5	-0.1	1
2907	1914-08-09	DEMING	NS	8201410	-61.18	45.22	16	16	16.1	-0.1	1
2908	1914-08-10	DEMING	NS	8201410	-61.18	45.22	16	16.6	17.2	-0.6	1
2909	1914-09-02	DEMING	NS	8201410	-61.18	45.22	16	17.3	17.8	-0.5	1
2910	1914-09-25	DEMING	NS	8201410	-61.18	45.22	16	18.2	18.3	-0.1	1
2911	1917-08-25	DEMING	NS	8201410	-61.18	45.22	16	21.8	22.2	-0.4	1
2912	1917-08-30	DEMING	NS	8201410	-61.18	45.22	16	20.4	21.6	-1.2	1
2913	1924-08-22	DEMING	NS	8201410	-61.18	45.22	16	19.4	20.5	-1.1	1
2914	1926-08-27	DEMING	NS	8201410	-61.18	45.22	16	18.4	20	-1.6	1
2915	1926-08-28	DEMING	NS	8201410	-61.18	45.22	16	17.5	18.4	-0.9	1
2916	1927-06-23	DEMING	NS	8201410	-61.18	45.22	16	12.9	13.3	-0.4	1
2917	1929-10-02	DEMING	NS	8201410	-61.18	45.22	16	10.6	10.8	-0.2	1
2918	1930-08-16	DEMING	NS	8201410	-61.18	45.22	16	19.5	20	-0.5	1
2919	1930-10-02	DEMING	NS	8201410	-61.18	45.22	16	13.4	14.1	-0.7	1
2920	1931-09-15	DEMING	NS	8201410	-61.18	45.22	16	17.2	17.8	-0.6	1
2921	1934-08-29	DEMING	NS	8201410	-61.18	45.22	16	17.1	17.3	-0.2	1
2922	1934-09-03	DEMING	NS	8201410	-61.18	45.22	16	17.5	18	-0.5	1
2923	1935-12-20	DEMING	NS	8201410	-61.18	45.22	16	-0.6	-0.3	-0.3	1

2924	1936-07-14	DEMING	NS	8201410	-61.18	45.22	16	15.4	16.5	-1.1	1
2925	1936-07-27	DEMING	NS	8201410	-61.18	45.22	16	21.4	22.4	-1	1
2926	1936-07-29	DEMING	NS	8201410	-61.18	45.22	16	20.8	22.4	-1.6	1
2927	1936-08-16	DEMING	NS	8201410	-61.18	45.22	16	18.2	19.1	-0.9	1
2928	1936-08-17	DEMING	NS	8201410	-61.18	45.22	16	14.8	16.5	-1.7	1
2929	1936-08-22	DEMING	NS	8201410	-61.18	45.22	16	17.1	17.2	-0.1	1
2930	1936-08-23	DEMING	NS	8201410	-61.18	45.22	16	17.1	18.5	-1.4	1
2931	1936-08-24	DEMING	NS	8201410	-61.18	45.22	16	17.1	17.9	-0.8	1
2932	1936-09-26	DEMING	NS	8201410	-61.18	45.22	16	16.6	17.3	-0.7	1
2933	1936-10-08	DEMING	NS	8201410	-61.18	45.22	16	14.9	15.1	-0.2	1
2934	1936-10-09	DEMING	NS	8201410	-61.18	45.22	16	14.9	17.3	-2.4	1
2935	1937-06-24	DEMING	NS	8201410	-61.18	45.22	16	14.9	15.8	-0.9	1
2936	1937-07-28	DEMING	NS	8201410	-61.18	45.22	16	17.1	17.9	-0.8	1
2937	1937-08-01	DEMING	NS	8201410	-61.18	45.22	16	18.9	19.1	-0.2	1
2938	1937-08-02	DEMING	NS	8201410	-61.18	45.22	16	18.2	18.5	-0.3	1
2939	1937-08-27	DEMING	NS	8201410	-61.18	45.22	16	17.1	17.2	-0.1	1
2940	1937-10-07	DEMING	NS	8201410	-61.18	45.22	16	16.6	17.2	-0.6	1
2941	1938-07-20	DEMING	NS	8201410	-61.18	45.22	16	17.1	17.3	-0.2	1
2942	1938-07-31	DEMING	NS	8201410	-61.18	45.22	16	17.5	17.9	-0.4	1
2943	1938-08-02	DEMING	NS	8201410	-61.18	45.22	16	17.5	17.9	-0.4	1
2944	1938-08-03	DEMING	NS	8201410	-61.18	45.22	16	20.6	20.7	-0.1	1
2945	1938-08-05	DEMING	NS	8201410	-61.18	45.22	16	17.5	18	-0.5	1
2946	1938-08-06	DEMING	NS	8201410	-61.18	45.22	16	18.2	19.6	-1.4	1
2947	1938-08-12	DEMING	NS	8201410	-61.18	45.22	16	17.2	19.1	-1.9	1
2948	1938-08-29	DEMING	NS	8201410	-61.18	45.22	16	19	19.1	-0.1	1
2949	1938-09-04	DEMING	NS	8201410	-61.18	45.22	16	17	17.3	-0.3	1
2950	1938-09-20	DEMING	NS	8201410	-61.18	45.22	16	18.2	18.5	-0.3	1
2951	1938-09-21	DEMING	NS	8201410	-61.18	45.22	16	18.2	19.1	-0.9	1
2952	1938-09-22	DEMING	NS	8201410	-61.18	45.22	16	19	19.1	-0.1	1
2953	1939-07-12	DEMING	NS	8201410	-61.18	45.22	16	13.9	14.4	-0.5	1
2954	1939-08-10	DEMING	NS	8201410	-61.18	45.22	16	18.8	19.6	-0.8	1
2955	1939-08-29	DEMING	NS	8201410	-61.18	45.22	16	18.9	20.7	-1.8	1
2956	1940-08-07	DEMING	NS	8201410	-61.18	45.22	16	17.1	17.9	-0.8	1
2957	1940-09-02	DEMING	NS	8201410	-61.18	45.22	16	17	18	-1	1

2958	1941-02-08	DEMING	NS	8201410	-61.18	45.22	16	-0.1	0.5	-0.6	1
2959	1941-02-09	DEMING	NS	8201410	-61.18	45.22	16	0.8	1.1	-0.3	1
2960	1941-02-11	DEMING	NS	8201410	-61.18	45.22	16	0.8	1.1	-0.3	1
2961	1941-08-02	DEMING	NS	8201410	-61.18	45.22	16	15.4	15.8	-0.4	1
2962	1941-08-16	DEMING	NS	8201410	-61.18	45.22	16	16.6	17.3	-0.7	1
2963	1941-08-17	DEMING	NS	8201410	-61.18	45.22	16	16.1	16.5	-0.4	1
2964	1941-08-26	DEMING	NS	8201410	-61.18	45.22	16	17.5	18	-0.5	1
2965	1941-08-27	DEMING	NS	8201410	-61.18	45.22	16	20.6	20.7	-0.1	1
2966	1941-10-06	DEMING	NS	8201410	-61.18	45.22	16	8.3	8.5	-0.2	1
2967	1942-03-26	DEMING	NS	8201410	-61.18	45.22	16	1.5	2.3	-0.8	1
2968	1942-10-27	DEMING	NS	8201410	-61.18	45.22	16	15.7	16.2	-0.5	1
2969	1943-04-20	DEMING	NS	8201410	-61.18	45.22	16	1	2	-1	1
2970	1943-04-23	DEMING	NS	8201410	-61.18	45.22	16	0.7	1	-0.3	1
2971	1943-10-02	DEMING	NS	8201410	-61.18	45.22	16	15.1	16.2	-1.1	1
2972	1944-01-21	DEMING	NS	8201410	-61.18	45.22	16	0.8	1	-0.2	1
2973	1944-11-22	DEMING	NS	8201410	-61.18	45.22	16	5.3	7.7	-2.4	1
2974	1945-11-01	DEMING	NS	8201410	-61.18	45.22	16	1.5	2.4	-0.9	1
2975	1945-11-02	DEMING	NS	8201410	-61.18	45.22	16	0.9	1.9	-1	1
2976	1945-11-08	DEMING	NS	8201410	-61.18	45.22	16	1.1	1.9	-0.8	1
2977	1946-09-25	DEMING	NS	8201410	-61.18	45.22	16	14.5	15	-0.5	1
2978	1948-08-05	DEMING	NS	8201410	-61.18	45.22	16	17.4	17.8	-0.4	1
2979	1954-07-15	DEMING	NS	8201410	-61.18	45.22	16	14.4	15.6	-1.2	1
2980	1955-12-13	DEMING	NS	8201410	-61.18	45.22	16	-1.7	-1.2	-0.5	1
2981	1956-01-17	DEMING	NS	8201410	-61.18	45.22	16	1.5	1.6	-0.1	1
2982	1956-08-08	DEMING	NS	8201410	-61.18	45.22	16	14.5	15	-0.5	1
2983	1956-09-13	DEMING	NS	8201410	-61.18	45.22	16	15.1	15.6	-0.5	1
2984	1956-11-08	DEMING	NS	8201410	-61.18	45.22	16	8	8.6	-0.6	1
2985	2008-10-14	BELLEVILLE	ONT	6150689	-77.4	44.15	76	11	12	-1	1
2986	2014-01-31	BELLEVILLE	ONT	6150689	-77.4	44.15	76	-4.5	-4	-0.5	1
2987	2010-12-23	SAULT STE MARIE	ONT	6057591	-84.52	46.48	192	-11	-7.7	-3.3	1
2988	1913-12-30	DRUMMONDVILLE	QUE	7022160	-72.48	45.88	82	-2.7	-2	-0.7	1
2989	1926-11-27	DRUMMONDVILLE	QUE	7022160	-72.48	45.88	82	-1	-0.7	-0.3	1
2990	1927-02-26	DRUMMONDVILLE	QUE	7022160	-72.48	45.88	82	-1.6	-1.3	-0.3	1
2991	1927-03-21	DRUMMONDVILLE	QUE	7022160	-72.48	45.88	82	-3.5	-3.4	-0.1	1

2992	1927-12-29	DRUMMONDVILLE	QUE	7022160	-72.48	45.88	82	3.3	3.7	-0.4	1
2993	1930-02-25	DRUMMONDVILLE	QUE	7022160	-72.48	45.88	82	-5.9	-5.4	-0.5	1
2994	1930-03-28	DRUMMONDVILLE	QUE	7022160	-72.48	45.88	82	-4.4	-3.4	-1	1
2995	1930-04-22	DRUMMONDVILLE	QUE	7022160	-72.48	45.88	82	-3.2	-1.3	-1.9	1
2996	1931-01-12	DRUMMONDVILLE	QUE	7022160	-72.48	45.88	82	-10.1	-3.4	-6.7	1
2997	1931-01-19	DRUMMONDVILLE	QUE	7022160	-72.48	45.88	82	-15.5	-9.6	-5.9	1
2998	1931-12-13	DRUMMONDVILLE	QUE	7022160	-72.48	45.88	82	-9.2	-2.9	-6.3	1
2999	1931-12-23	DRUMMONDVILLE	QUE	7022160	-72.48	45.88	82	-0.3	0.1	-0.4	1
3000	1931-12-24	DRUMMONDVILLE	QUE	7022160	-72.48	45.88	82	-6.7	-3.4	-3.3	1
3001	1932-04-11	DRUMMONDVILLE	QUE	7022160	-72.48	45.88	82	2.8	3.2	-0.4	1
3002	1932-11-15	DRUMMONDVILLE	QUE	7022160	-72.48	45.88	82	-0.3	0	-0.3	1
3003	1932-12-07	DRUMMONDVILLE	QUE	7022160	-72.48	45.88	82	-4.8	-4.4	-0.4	1
3004	1933-01-25	DRUMMONDVILLE	QUE	7022160	-72.48	45.88	82	-4.7	-3.2	-1.5	1
3005	1933-01-27	DRUMMONDVILLE	QUE	7022160	-72.48	45.88	82	-2.2	-1.5	-0.7	1
3006	1933-02-08	DRUMMONDVILLE	QUE	7022160	-72.48	45.88	82	-13.3	-8.1	-5.2	1
3007	1933-02-15	DRUMMONDVILLE	QUE	7022160	-72.48	45.88	82	-8.7	-7.2	-1.5	1
3008	1933-03-09	DRUMMONDVILLE	QUE	7022160	-72.48	45.88	82	-10.6	-6.2	-4.4	1
3009	1933-03-21	DRUMMONDVILLE	QUE	7022160	-72.48	45.88	82	-1.5	-0.8	-0.7	1
3010	1933-04-07	DRUMMONDVILLE	QUE	7022160	-72.48	45.88	82	2.8	3.6	-0.8	1
3011	1933-10-12	DRUMMONDVILLE	QUE	7022160	-72.48	45.88	82	11.2	12	-0.8	1
3012	1933-10-22	DRUMMONDVILLE	QUE	7022160	-72.48	45.88	82	1	5.6	-4.6	1
3013	1933-11-03	DRUMMONDVILLE	QUE	7022160	-72.48	45.88	82	1	7	-6	1
3014	1933-11-21	DRUMMONDVILLE	QUE	7022160	-72.48	45.88	82	-7.4	-4.6	-2.8	1
3015	1934-01-25	DRUMMONDVILLE	QUE	7022160	-72.48	45.88	82	-13.9	-12.7	-1.2	1
3016	1934-01-28	DRUMMONDVILLE	QUE	7022160	-72.48	45.88	82	-25.3	-21	-4.3	1
3017	1934-02-12	DRUMMONDVILLE	QUE	7022160	-72.48	45.88	82	-10	-7.1	-2.9	1
3018	1934-02-22	DRUMMONDVILLE	QUE	7022160	-72.48	45.88	82	-17	-13.3	-3.7	1
3019	1934-03-18	DRUMMONDVILLE	QUE	7022160	-72.48	45.88	82	-8.6	-8.4	-0.2	1
3020	1934-12-12	DRUMMONDVILLE	QUE	7022160	-72.48	45.88	82	-18.7	-18.3	-0.4	1
3021	1935-12-12	DRUMMONDVILLE	QUE	7022160	-72.48	45.88	82	-0.5	-0.3	-0.2	1
3022	1935-12-15	DRUMMONDVILLE	QUE	7022160	-72.48	45.88	82	-2.1	-1.5	-0.6	1
3023	2002-12-23	DRUMMONDVILLE	QUE	7022160	-72.48	45.88	82	-4	0	-4	1
3024	2010-11-23	DRUMMONDVILLE	QUE	7022160	-72.48	45.88	82	1	3.5	-2.5	1
3025	2011-01-29	DRUMMONDVILLE	QUE	7022160	-72.48	45.88	82	-9	-8	-1	1

3026	1888-01-16	HALIFAX	NS	8202251	-63.58	44.65	145	6	6.1	-0.1	1
3027	1932-10-19	HALIFAX	NS	8202251	-63.58	44.65	145	8.9	9	-0.1	1
3028	1945-11-21	LIVERPOOL	NS	8203100	-64.93	44.13	50	-0.7	-0.6	-0.1	1
3029	1946-05-26	LIVERPOOL	NS	8203100	-64.93	44.13	50	15.2	15.6	-0.4	1
3030	1955-09-12	LIVERPOOL	NS	8203100	-64.93	44.13	50	16.6	16.7	-0.1	1
3031	2006-05-05	LIVERPOOL	NS	8203100	-64.93	44.13	50	0	8	-8	1
3032	2007-03-21	LIVERPOOL	NS	8203100	-64.93	44.13	50	1	5.5	-4.5	1
3033	2009-12-11	LIVERPOOL	NS	8203100	-64.93	44.13	50	-3.5	-1.7	-1.8	1
3034	2008-11-16	YELLOW GRASS	SASK	4019040	-104.18	49.82	580	-2	-1	-1	1
3035	1989-11-03	MCINNES ISLAND	BC	1065010	-128.72	52.27	26	0.8	9.1	-8.3	1
3036	2007-03-06	MCINNES ISLAND	BC	1065010	-128.72	52.27	26	7.4	9.6	-2.2	1
3037	2007-09-08	MCINNES ISLAND	BC	1065010	-128.72	52.27	26	13.5	13.8	-0.3	1
3038	2008-01-18	MCINNES ISLAND	BC	1065010	-128.72	52.27	26	5.8	8	-2.2	1
3039	2008-04-07	MCINNES ISLAND	BC	1065010	-128.72	52.27	26	4.3	4.7	-0.4	1
3040	2008-05-23	MCINNES ISLAND	BC	1065010	-128.72	52.27	26	10	10.8	-0.8	1
3041	2010-06-11	MCINNES ISLAND	BC	1065010	-128.72	52.27	26	1.5	10	-8.5	1
3042	2010-08-12	MCINNES ISLAND	BC	1065010	-128.72	52.27	26	10.8	12	-1.2	1
3043	2010-11-19	MCINNES ISLAND	BC	1065010	-128.72	52.27	26	-0.2	13.8	-14	1
3044	2011-06-22	MCINNES ISLAND	BC	1065010	-128.72	52.27	26	10.5	12	-1.5	1
3045	2011-10-29	MCINNES ISLAND	BC	1065010	-128.72	52.27	26	7.6	8.7	-1.1	1
3046	2011-11-26	MCINNES ISLAND	BC	1065010	-128.72	52.27	26	1	9	-8	1
3047	2012-06-17	MCINNES ISLAND	BC	1065010	-128.72	52.27	26	10.8	17.2	-6.4	1
3048	2014-01-22	MCINNES ISLAND	BC	1065010	-128.72	52.27	26	5.2	5.4	-0.2	1
3049	2014-05-03	MCINNES ISLAND	BC	1065010	-128.72	52.27	26	9	9.2	-0.2	1
3050	2014-08-09	MCINNES ISLAND	BC	1065010	-128.72	52.27	26	2.2	12.4	-10.2	1
3051	2007-12-11	SANDSPIT	BC	1057050	-131.82	53.25	6	4	5	-1	1
3052	2011-02-26	SANDSPIT	BC	1057050	-131.82	53.25	6	2	4	-2	1
3053	1910-10-18	STEWART	BC	1067742	-129.98	55.93	7	7	7.8	-0.8	1
3054	1910-10-19	STEWART	BC	1067742	-129.98	55.93	7	7.4	7.6	-0.2	1
3055	1910-10-20	STEWART	BC	1067742	-129.98	55.93	7	7	7.6	-0.6	1
3056	1910-12-05	STEWART	BC	1067742	-129.98	55.93	7	-4	-3.7	-0.3	1
3057	1910-12-24	STEWART	BC	1067742	-129.98	55.93	7	-0.2	-0.1	-0.1	1
3058	1910-12-25	STEWART	BC	1067742	-129.98	55.93	7	1.3	2.2	-0.9	1
3059	1911-01-01	STEWART	BC	1067742	-129.98	55.93	7	-14	-8.3	-5.7	1

3060	1911-01-02	STEWART	BC	1067742	-129.98	55.93	7	-10.6	-7.3	-3.3	1
3061	1911-01-03	STEWART	BC	1067742	-129.98	55.93	7	-5.8	-5.1	-0.7	1
3062	1911-01-10	STEWART	BC	1067742	-129.98	55.93	7	-16.2	-14.9	-1.3	1
3063	1911-01-11	STEWART	BC	1067742	-129.98	55.93	7	-21.2	-14.9	-6.3	1
3064	1911-01-12	STEWART	BC	1067742	-129.98	55.93	7	-19	-12.6	-6.4	1
3065	1911-01-13	STEWART	BC	1067742	-129.98	55.93	7	-17.4	-16.5	-0.9	1
3066	1911-01-14	STEWART	BC	1067742	-129.98	55.93	7	-19.6	-13.8	-5.8	1
3067	1911-01-15	STEWART	BC	1067742	-129.98	55.93	7	-11.8	-11.2	-0.6	1
3068	1911-01-17	STEWART	BC	1067742	-129.98	55.93	7	-5.2	-4.1	-1.1	1
3069	1911-01-19	STEWART	BC	1067742	-129.98	55.93	7	-11.1	-9	-2.1	1
3070	1911-01-20	STEWART	BC	1067742	-129.98	55.93	7	-12.4	-8.2	-4.2	1
3071	1911-01-21	STEWART	BC	1067742	-129.98	55.93	7	-10	-9.3	-0.7	1
3072	1911-01-22	STEWART	BC	1067742	-129.98	55.93	7	-11.8	-9.4	-2.4	1
3073	1911-01-23	STEWART	BC	1067742	-129.98	55.93	7	-6.5	-6.2	-0.3	1
3074	1911-01-26	STEWART	BC	1067742	-129.98	55.93	7	-12.9	-10.3	-2.6	1
3075	1911-01-27	STEWART	BC	1067742	-129.98	55.93	7	-16.2	-15.4	-0.8	1
3076	1911-01-28	STEWART	BC	1067742	-129.98	55.93	7	-21.2	-15.4	-5.8	1
3077	1911-01-29	STEWART	BC	1067742	-129.98	55.93	7	-16.2	-13.8	-2.4	1
3078	1911-01-30	STEWART	BC	1067742	-129.98	55.93	7	-13.5	-8.6	-4.9	1
3079	1911-01-31	STEWART	BC	1067742	-129.98	55.93	7	-10.6	-8.2	-2.4	1
3080	1911-02-02	STEWART	BC	1067742	-129.98	55.93	7	-18.5	-14.9	-3.6	1
3081	1911-02-03	STEWART	BC	1067742	-129.98	55.93	7	-15.1	-11.6	-3.5	1
3082	1911-02-05	STEWART	BC	1067742	-129.98	55.93	7	-6.5	-3.1	-3.4	1
3083	1911-02-07	STEWART	BC	1067742	-129.98	55.93	7	-10	-9.1	-0.9	1
3084	1911-02-08	STEWART	BC	1067742	-129.98	55.93	7	-5.8	-5.6	-0.2	1
3085	1911-02-09	STEWART	BC	1067742	-129.98	55.93	7	-4.5	-3.1	-1.4	1
3086	1911-03-12	STEWART	BC	1067742	-129.98	55.93	7	0.9	1.4	-0.5	1
3087	1911-03-18	STEWART	BC	1067742	-129.98	55.93	7	3.8	4.5	-0.7	1
3088	1911-03-19	STEWART	BC	1067742	-129.98	55.93	7	3.8	4.5	-0.7	1
3089	1911-04-15	STEWART	BC	1067742	-129.98	55.93	7	1.2	2.3	-1.1	1
3090	1911-07-11	STEWART	BC	1067742	-129.98	55.93	7	17.6	18.7	-1.1	1
3091	1911-07-23	STEWART	BC	1067742	-129.98	55.93	7	12.4	12.6	-0.2	1
3092	1911-08-29	STEWART	BC	1067742	-129.98	55.93	7	11.5	11.9	-0.4	1
3093	1911-08-30	STEWART	BC	1067742	-129.98	55.93	7	11.3	11.9	-0.6	1

3094	1911-10-18	STEWART	BC	1067742	-129.98	55.93	7	6.9	7.1	-0.2	1
3095	1911-11-01	STEWART	BC	1067742	-129.98	55.93	7	6	7.7	-1.7	1
3096	1911-11-02	STEWART	BC	1067742	-129.98	55.93	7	7.3	7.6	-0.3	1
3097	1911-11-04	STEWART	BC	1067742	-129.98	55.93	7	6.9	7.6	-0.7	1
3098	1911-11-08	STEWART	BC	1067742	-129.98	55.93	7	-7.2	-6.6	-0.6	1
3099	1911-11-10	STEWART	BC	1067742	-129.98	55.93	7	-8.9	-7.2	-1.7	1
3100	1911-11-11	STEWART	BC	1067742	-129.98	55.93	7	-7.2	-7.1	-0.1	1
3101	1911-11-12	STEWART	BC	1067742	-129.98	55.93	7	-7.2	-6.6	-0.6	1
3102	1911-11-13	STEWART	BC	1067742	-129.98	55.93	7	-8.9	-7.7	-1.2	1
3103	1911-11-14	STEWART	BC	1067742	-129.98	55.93	7	-13.5	-10.3	-3.2	1
3104	1911-11-16	STEWART	BC	1067742	-129.98	55.93	7	-5.3	-4.2	-1.1	1
3105	1911-11-21	STEWART	BC	1067742	-129.98	55.93	7	-2.5	-1.6	-0.9	1
3106	1911-11-30	STEWART	BC	1067742	-129.98	55.93	7	1.2	2.7	-1.5	1
3107	1911-12-01	STEWART	BC	1067742	-129.98	55.93	7	1.7	2.6	-0.9	1
3108	1911-12-02	STEWART	BC	1067742	-129.98	55.93	7	1.7	2.7	-1	1
3109	1911-12-03	STEWART	BC	1067742	-129.98	55.93	7	0.8	2.7	-1.9	1
3110	1911-12-14	STEWART	BC	1067742	-129.98	55.93	7	1.2	3.3	-2.1	1
3111	1911-12-17	STEWART	BC	1067742	-129.98	55.93	7	-2.4	-2.1	-0.3	1
3112	1911-12-18	STEWART	BC	1067742	-129.98	55.93	7	-1.7	-0.7	-1	1
3113	1911-12-22	STEWART	BC	1067742	-129.98	55.93	7	-0.2	0.8	-1	1
3114	1911-12-26	STEWART	BC	1067742	-129.98	55.93	7	-7.7	-4.1	-3.6	1
3115	1911-12-27	STEWART	BC	1067742	-129.98	55.93	7	-2.5	-2.2	-0.3	1
3116	1911-12-30	STEWART	BC	1067742	-129.98	55.93	7	-19	-13.2	-5.8	1
3117	1911-12-31	STEWART	BC	1067742	-129.98	55.93	7	-19	-13.2	-5.8	1
3118	1912-01-01	STEWART	BC	1067742	-129.98	55.93	7	-19	-13.8	-5.2	1
3119	1912-01-02	STEWART	BC	1067742	-129.98	55.93	7	-19	-12.6	-6.4	1
3120	1912-01-03	STEWART	BC	1067742	-129.98	55.93	7	-13.5	-8.9	-4.6	1
3121	1912-01-04	STEWART	BC	1067742	-129.98	55.93	7	-11.2	-8.5	-2.7	1
3122	1912-01-05	STEWART	BC	1067742	-129.98	55.93	7	-7.2	-6.3	-0.9	1
3123	1912-01-06	STEWART	BC	1067742	-129.98	55.93	7	-7.2	-6.9	-0.3	1
3124	1912-01-07	STEWART	BC	1067742	-129.98	55.93	7	-11.8	-7.6	-4.2	1
3125	1912-01-08	STEWART	BC	1067742	-129.98	55.93	7	-12.4	-12.2	-0.2	1
3126	1912-01-09	STEWART	BC	1067742	-129.98	55.93	7	-10.6	-7.2	-3.4	1
3127	1912-01-11	STEWART	BC	1067742	-129.98	55.93	7	-20.1	-16	-4.1	1

3128	1912-01-12	STEWART	BC	1067742	-129.98	55.93	7	-14	-11.6	-2.4	1
3129	1912-01-13	STEWART	BC	1067742	-129.98	55.93	7	-11.8	-10.7	-1.1	1
3130	1912-01-14	STEWART	BC	1067742	-129.98	55.93	7	-9.5	-8.6	-0.9	1
3131	1912-01-17	STEWART	BC	1067742	-129.98	55.93	7	-10	-9.4	-0.6	1
3132	1912-01-18	STEWART	BC	1067742	-129.98	55.93	7	-8.4	-7.5	-0.9	1
3133	1912-01-19	STEWART	BC	1067742	-129.98	55.93	7	-8.4	-7.5	-0.9	1
3134	1912-01-21	STEWART	BC	1067742	-129.98	55.93	7	-3.9	-2.7	-1.2	1
3135	1912-02-13	STEWART	BC	1067742	-129.98	55.93	7	1.7	2.1	-0.4	1
3136	1912-02-22	STEWART	BC	1067742	-129.98	55.93	7	1.7	2.5	-0.8	1
3137	1912-06-01	STEWART	BC	1067742	-129.98	55.93	7	6.9	7.8	-0.9	1
3138	1912-06-02	STEWART	BC	1067742	-129.98	55.93	7	7.3	7.5	-0.2	1
3139	1912-10-10	STEWART	BC	1067742	-129.98	55.93	7	7.8	8	-0.2	1
3140	1912-10-11	STEWART	BC	1067742	-129.98	55.93	7	7.4	7.6	-0.2	1
3141	1912-10-17	STEWART	BC	1067742	-129.98	55.93	7	6	7.6	-1.6	1
3142	1912-10-18	STEWART	BC	1067742	-129.98	55.93	7	6.5	7.5	-1	1
3143	1912-10-22	STEWART	BC	1067742	-129.98	55.93	7	6	6.4	-0.4	1
3144	1912-10-23	STEWART	BC	1067742	-129.98	55.93	7	5.4	7.1	-1.7	1
3145	1912-10-25	STEWART	BC	1067742	-129.98	55.93	7	7	8	-1	1
3146	1912-10-28	STEWART	BC	1067742	-129.98	55.93	7	7.8	8	-0.2	1
3147	1912-11-23	STEWART	BC	1067742	-129.98	55.93	7	0.7	0.8	-0.1	1
3148	1912-11-27	STEWART	BC	1067742	-129.98	55.93	7	2.4	2.9	-0.5	1
3149	1912-12-01	STEWART	BC	1067742	-129.98	55.93	7	-5.8	-2.2	-3.6	1
3150	1912-12-02	STEWART	BC	1067742	-129.98	55.93	7	-3.9	-1.7	-2.2	1
3151	1912-12-04	STEWART	BC	1067742	-129.98	55.93	7	3	6.4	-3.4	1
3152	1912-12-05	STEWART	BC	1067742	-129.98	55.93	7	3	7.4	-4.4	1
3153	1912-12-06	STEWART	BC	1067742	-129.98	55.93	7	2.3	6.4	-4.1	1
3154	1912-12-07	STEWART	BC	1067742	-129.98	55.93	7	2.3	6.4	-4.1	1
3155	1912-12-16	STEWART	BC	1067742	-129.98	55.93	7	-5.2	-4.6	-0.6	1
3156	1912-12-31	STEWART	BC	1067742	-129.98	55.93	7	-3.2	-3.1	-0.1	1
3157	1913-01-04	STEWART	BC	1067742	-129.98	55.93	7	-8.4	-5.6	-2.8	1
3158	1913-01-05	STEWART	BC	1067742	-129.98	55.93	7	-6.5	-4.1	-2.4	1
3159	1913-01-09	STEWART	BC	1067742	-129.98	55.93	7	-16.8	-14.3	-2.5	1
3160	1913-01-10	STEWART	BC	1067742	-129.98	55.93	7	-19.6	-14.3	-5.3	1
3161	1913-01-11	STEWART	BC	1067742	-129.98	55.93	7	-18.5	-14.3	-4.2	1

3162	1913-01-12	STEWART	BC	1067742	-129.98	55.93	7	-16.8	-13.2	-3.6	1
3163	1913-01-13	STEWART	BC	1067742	-129.98	55.93	7	-17.4	-15.4	-2	1
3164	1913-01-14	STEWART	BC	1067742	-129.98	55.93	7	-16.8	-11.6	-5.2	1
3165	1913-01-15	STEWART	BC	1067742	-129.98	55.93	7	-14	-9.4	-4.6	1
3166	1913-01-17	STEWART	BC	1067742	-129.98	55.93	7	-21.8	-20.4	-1.4	1
3167	1913-01-18	STEWART	BC	1067742	-129.98	55.93	7	-18.5	-13.2	-5.3	1
3168	1913-01-19	STEWART	BC	1067742	-129.98	55.93	7	-17.4	-10.3	-7.1	1
3169	1913-01-20	STEWART	BC	1067742	-129.98	55.93	7	-14	-8.5	-5.5	1
3170	1913-01-21	STEWART	BC	1067742	-129.98	55.93	7	-10	-7.3	-2.7	1
3171	1913-01-22	STEWART	BC	1067742	-129.98	55.93	7	-5.8	-5	-0.8	1
3172	1913-01-26	STEWART	BC	1067742	-129.98	55.93	7	0.7	0.8	-0.1	1
3173	1913-01-29	STEWART	BC	1067742	-129.98	55.93	7	1.3	2.8	-1.5	1
3174	1913-01-30	STEWART	BC	1067742	-129.98	55.93	7	0.7	3	-2.3	1
3175	1913-02-16	STEWART	BC	1067742	-129.98	55.93	7	1.3	3	-1.7	1
3176	1913-03-06	STEWART	BC	1067742	-129.98	55.93	7	0.7	2.9	-2.2	1
3177	1913-03-07	STEWART	BC	1067742	-129.98	55.93	7	2.3	2.8	-0.5	1
3178	1913-03-17	STEWART	BC	1067742	-129.98	55.93	7	-8.4	-8.3	-0.1	1
3179	1913-08-25	STEWART	BC	1067742	-129.98	55.93	7	11.6	12.6	-1	1
3180	1913-08-26	STEWART	BC	1067742	-129.98	55.93	7	11.6	12.6	-1	1
3181	1913-08-27	STEWART	BC	1067742	-129.98	55.93	7	11.6	11.9	-0.3	1
3182	1913-09-28	STEWART	BC	1067742	-129.98	55.93	7	10.5	12	-1.5	1
3183	1913-10-10	STEWART	BC	1067742	-129.98	55.93	7	4.7	6.4	-1.7	1
3184	1913-10-11	STEWART	BC	1067742	-129.98	55.93	7	4.7	6.4	-1.7	1
3185	1913-10-18	STEWART	BC	1067742	-129.98	55.93	7	4	6.4	-2.4	1
3186	1913-10-23	STEWART	BC	1067742	-129.98	55.93	7	7	7.1	-0.1	1
3187	1913-10-25	STEWART	BC	1067742	-129.98	55.93	7	6.5	7.5	-1	1
3188	1913-10-26	STEWART	BC	1067742	-129.98	55.93	7	6.5	7.4	-0.9	1
3189	1913-10-28	STEWART	BC	1067742	-129.98	55.93	7	4.7	7.1	-2.4	1
3190	1913-11-03	STEWART	BC	1067742	-129.98	55.93	7	3	4.1	-1.1	1
3191	1913-11-05	STEWART	BC	1067742	-129.98	55.93	7	2.3	2.4	-0.1	1
3192	1913-11-09	STEWART	BC	1067742	-129.98	55.93	7	7.3	7.8	-0.5	1
3193	1913-11-10	STEWART	BC	1067742	-129.98	55.93	7	6.1	7.1	-1	1
3194	1913-11-11	STEWART	BC	1067742	-129.98	55.93	7	5.4	7.5	-2.1	1
3195	1913-11-12	STEWART	BC	1067742	-129.98	55.93	7	6.1	7.5	-1.4	1

3196	1913-11-13	STEWART	BC	1067742	-129.98	55.93	7	6.1	7.5	-1.4	1
3197	1913-11-14	STEWART	BC	1067742	-129.98	55.93	7	3	7.5	-4.5	1
3198	1913-12-01	STEWART	BC	1067742	-129.98	55.93	7	0.4	1.3	-0.9	1
3199	1913-12-02	STEWART	BC	1067742	-129.98	55.93	7	0.8	1.3	-0.5	1
3200	1913-12-07	STEWART	BC	1067742	-129.98	55.93	7	0.7	1.2	-0.5	1
3201	1913-12-08	STEWART	BC	1067742	-129.98	55.93	7	0.4	1.2	-0.8	1
3202	1913-12-09	STEWART	BC	1067742	-129.98	55.93	7	0.4	1.2	-0.8	1
3203	1913-12-10	STEWART	BC	1067742	-129.98	55.93	7	0.7	1.3	-0.6	1
3204	1913-12-13	STEWART	BC	1067742	-129.98	55.93	7	-3.2	-1.6	-1.6	1
3205	1913-12-15	STEWART	BC	1067742	-129.98	55.93	7	0.4	1.3	-0.9	1
3206	1913-12-18	STEWART	BC	1067742	-129.98	55.93	7	-5.8	-5.5	-0.3	1
3207	1913-12-19	STEWART	BC	1067742	-129.98	55.93	7	-8.4	-5.5	-2.9	1
3208	1913-12-20	STEWART	BC	1067742	-129.98	55.93	7	-8.4	-5.9	-2.5	1
3209	1913-12-21	STEWART	BC	1067742	-129.98	55.93	7	-5.2	-5.1	-0.1	1
3210	1913-12-22	STEWART	BC	1067742	-129.98	55.93	7	-5.2	-3.2	-2	1
3211	1913-12-24	STEWART	BC	1067742	-129.98	55.93	7	-5.2	-4.7	-0.5	1
3212	1913-12-25	STEWART	BC	1067742	-129.98	55.93	7	-4.5	-2.7	-1.8	1
3213	1913-12-26	STEWART	BC	1067742	-129.98	55.93	7	-3.8	-1.6	-2.2	1
3214	1914-01-09	STEWART	BC	1067742	-129.98	55.93	7	-3.2	-1.7	-1.5	1
3215	1914-01-11	STEWART	BC	1067742	-129.98	55.93	7	1.7	3.3	-1.6	1
3216	1914-01-15	STEWART	BC	1067742	-129.98	55.93	7	-5.8	-4.7	-1.1	1
3217	1914-01-19	STEWART	BC	1067742	-129.98	55.93	7	-9.5	-7.3	-2.2	1
3218	1914-01-23	STEWART	BC	1067742	-129.98	55.93	7	-14	-11.6	-2.4	1
3219	1914-01-24	STEWART	BC	1067742	-129.98	55.93	7	-14	-10.7	-3.3	1
3220	1914-01-25	STEWART	BC	1067742	-129.98	55.93	7	-9.5	-7.3	-2.2	1
3221	1914-01-27	STEWART	BC	1067742	-129.98	55.93	7	-12.4	-12.2	-0.2	1
3222	1914-01-28	STEWART	BC	1067742	-129.98	55.93	7	-14	-9.5	-4.5	1
3223	1914-01-29	STEWART	BC	1067742	-129.98	55.93	7	-10.6	-7.7	-2.9	1
3224	1914-01-30	STEWART	BC	1067742	-129.98	55.93	7	-7.7	-4.7	-3	1
3225	1914-02-02	STEWART	BC	1067742	-129.98	55.93	7	-5.3	-4.7	-0.6	1
3226	1914-02-04	STEWART	BC	1067742	-129.98	55.93	7	-10	-7.3	-2.7	1
3227	1914-02-05	STEWART	BC	1067742	-129.98	55.93	7	-8.9	-6.1	-2.8	1
3228	1914-02-06	STEWART	BC	1067742	-129.98	55.93	7	-6.5	-4.7	-1.8	1
3229	1914-02-13	STEWART	BC	1067742	-129.98	55.93	7	1.3	1.5	-0.2	1

3230	1914-03-01	STEWART	BC	1067742	-129.98	55.93	7	2.3	2.8	-0.5	1
3231	1914-03-02	STEWART	BC	1067742	-129.98	55.93	7	1.7	2.7	-1	1
3232	1914-03-03	STEWART	BC	1067742	-129.98	55.93	7	2.3	2.7	-0.4	1
3233	1914-07-21	STEWART	BC	1067742	-129.98	55.93	7	10.1	11.3	-1.2	1
3234	1914-08-05	STEWART	BC	1067742	-129.98	55.93	7	11.6	11.9	-0.3	1
3235	1914-09-05	STEWART	BC	1067742	-129.98	55.93	7	10.8	11.3	-0.5	1
3236	1914-09-07	STEWART	BC	1067742	-129.98	55.93	7	12.5	12.6	-0.1	1
3237	1914-09-22	STEWART	BC	1067742	-129.98	55.93	7	11.3	12.6	-1.3	1
3238	1914-09-24	STEWART	BC	1067742	-129.98	55.93	7	11.5	12	-0.5	1
3239	1914-10-05	STEWART	BC	1067742	-129.98	55.93	7	9.1	10	-0.9	1
3240	1914-10-06	STEWART	BC	1067742	-129.98	55.93	7	10.1	11.2	-1.1	1
3241	1914-10-10	STEWART	BC	1067742	-129.98	55.93	7	10.1	11.2	-1.1	1
3242	1914-10-14	STEWART	BC	1067742	-129.98	55.93	7	10.9	11.2	-0.3	1
3243	1914-11-01	STEWART	BC	1067742	-129.98	55.93	7	7.3	7.8	-0.5	1
3244	1914-11-13	STEWART	BC	1067742	-129.98	55.93	7	-2.5	-2.2	-0.3	1
3245	1914-11-15	STEWART	BC	1067742	-129.98	55.93	7	-5.2	-4.2	-1	1
3246	1914-11-16	STEWART	BC	1067742	-129.98	55.93	7	-4.6	-2.2	-2.4	1
3247	1914-12-03	STEWART	BC	1067742	-129.98	55.93	7	-9.5	-7.3	-2.2	1
3248	1914-12-04	STEWART	BC	1067742	-129.98	55.93	7	-9.5	-6.9	-2.6	1
3249	1914-12-06	STEWART	BC	1067742	-129.98	55.93	7	-7.2	-4.6	-2.6	1
3250	1914-12-07	STEWART	BC	1067742	-129.98	55.93	7	-6.5	-6.3	-0.2	1
3251	1914-12-08	STEWART	BC	1067742	-129.98	55.93	7	-6.5	-5.1	-1.4	1
3252	1914-12-09	STEWART	BC	1067742	-129.98	55.93	7	-8.4	-6.2	-2.2	1
3253	1914-12-10	STEWART	BC	1067742	-129.98	55.93	7	-8.9	-6.2	-2.7	1
3254	1914-12-11	STEWART	BC	1067742	-129.98	55.93	7	-8.9	-6.3	-2.6	1
3255	1914-12-12	STEWART	BC	1067742	-129.98	55.93	7	-9.5	-7.2	-2.3	1
3256	1914-12-13	STEWART	BC	1067742	-129.98	55.93	7	-11.1	-7.2	-3.9	1
3257	1914-12-14	STEWART	BC	1067742	-129.98	55.93	7	-10.6	-7.5	-3.1	1
3258	1914-12-15	STEWART	BC	1067742	-129.98	55.93	7	-11.8	-8	-3.8	1
3259	1914-12-16	STEWART	BC	1067742	-129.98	55.93	7	-8.9	-7.5	-1.4	1
3260	1914-12-17	STEWART	BC	1067742	-129.98	55.93	7	-7.7	-5.9	-1.8	1
3261	1914-12-19	STEWART	BC	1067742	-129.98	55.93	7	-7.7	-7.3	-0.4	1
3262	1914-12-28	STEWART	BC	1067742	-129.98	55.93	7	-8.9	-8.6	-0.3	1
3263	1914-12-30	STEWART	BC	1067742	-129.98	55.93	7	-2.5	-2.2	-0.3	1

3264	1915-01-21	STEWART	BC	1067742	-129.98	55.93	7	-5.3	-4.6	-0.7	1
3265	1915-01-26	STEWART	BC	1067742	-129.98	55.93	7	-8.9	-8.3	-0.6	1
3266	1915-01-27	STEWART	BC	1067742	-129.98	55.93	7	-7.7	-6.3	-1.4	1
3267	1915-03-09	STEWART	BC	1067742	-129.98	55.93	7	2.3	2.8	-0.5	1
3268	1915-03-17	STEWART	BC	1067742	-129.98	55.93	7	3	3.2	-0.2	1
3269	1915-04-01	STEWART	BC	1067742	-129.98	55.93	7	5.4	6.4	-1	1
3270	1915-04-14	STEWART	BC	1067742	-129.98	55.93	7	7	7.7	-0.7	1
3271	1915-04-15	STEWART	BC	1067742	-129.98	55.93	7	7	7.1	-0.1	1
3272	1915-07-21	STEWART	BC	1067742	-129.98	55.93	7	14.9	17	-2.1	1
3273	1915-11-10	STEWART	BC	1067742	-129.98	55.93	7	-3.2	-2.7	-0.5	1
3274	1915-11-13	STEWART	BC	1067742	-129.98	55.93	7	-3.2	-2.7	-0.5	1
3275	1915-12-07	STEWART	BC	1067742	-129.98	55.93	7	2.3	2.7	-0.4	1
3276	1915-12-15	STEWART	BC	1067742	-129.98	55.93	7	-2.5	-1.5	-1	1
3277	1915-12-26	STEWART	BC	1067742	-129.98	55.93	7	-5.8	-4.1	-1.7	1
3278	1916-01-03	STEWART	BC	1067742	-129.98	55.93	7	-13.5	-11.6	-1.9	1
3279	1916-01-09	STEWART	BC	1067742	-129.98	55.93	7	-16.8	-11.6	-5.2	1
3280	1916-01-10	STEWART	BC	1067742	-129.98	55.93	7	-17.4	-12.2	-5.2	1
3281	1916-01-11	STEWART	BC	1067742	-129.98	55.93	7	-12.4	-11.6	-0.8	1
3282	1916-01-12	STEWART	BC	1067742	-129.98	55.93	7	-12.4	-9.4	-3	1
3283	1916-01-21	STEWART	BC	1067742	-129.98	55.93	7	-12.4	-11.6	-0.8	1
3284	1916-01-22	STEWART	BC	1067742	-129.98	55.93	7	-19	-14.9	-4.1	1
3285	1916-01-23	STEWART	BC	1067742	-129.98	55.93	7	-17.9	-17.6	-0.3	1
3286	1916-01-26	STEWART	BC	1067742	-129.98	55.93	7	-10.6	-8	-2.6	1
3287	1916-01-27	STEWART	BC	1067742	-129.98	55.93	7	-12.4	-7.9	-4.5	1
3288	1916-01-28	STEWART	BC	1067742	-129.98	55.93	7	-11.2	-8	-3.2	1
3289	1916-02-10	STEWART	BC	1067742	-129.98	55.93	7	-8.4	-5.8	-2.6	1
3290	1916-02-11	STEWART	BC	1067742	-129.98	55.93	7	-7.7	-5.6	-2.1	1
3291	1916-02-12	STEWART	BC	1067742	-129.98	55.93	7	-7.2	-5.6	-1.6	1
3292	1916-02-13	STEWART	BC	1067742	-129.98	55.93	7	-5.2	-3.1	-2.1	1
3293	1916-03-03	STEWART	BC	1067742	-129.98	55.93	7	-7.2	-6.2	-1	1
3294	1916-03-04	STEWART	BC	1067742	-129.98	55.93	7	-6.5	-6.2	-0.3	1
3295	1916-03-18	STEWART	BC	1067742	-129.98	55.93	7	3	7.5	-4.5	1
3296	1916-05-05	STEWART	BC	1067742	-129.98	55.93	7	7	7.1	-0.1	1
3297	1916-06-06	STEWART	BC	1067742	-129.98	55.93	7	10	10.4	-0.4	1

3298	1916-06-14	STEWART	BC	1067742	-129.98	55.93	7	11.5	12.6	-1.1	1
3299	1916-07-05	STEWART	BC	1067742	-129.98	55.93	7	10.4	11.9	-1.5	1
3300	1916-07-14	STEWART	BC	1067742	-129.98	55.93	7	11.1	12	-0.9	1
3301	1916-07-28	STEWART	BC	1067742	-129.98	55.93	7	15.3	15.4	-0.1	1
3302	1916-07-29	STEWART	BC	1067742	-129.98	55.93	7	12.8	14.3	-1.5	1
3303	1916-08-14	STEWART	BC	1067742	-129.98	55.93	7	12.9	13.7	-0.8	1
3304	1916-08-23	STEWART	BC	1067742	-129.98	55.93	7	10.9	11.9	-1	1
3305	1916-09-09	STEWART	BC	1067742	-129.98	55.93	7	10	11.3	-1.3	1
3306	1916-09-21	STEWART	BC	1067742	-129.98	55.93	7	9.6	9.8	-0.2	1
3307	1916-10-19	STEWART	BC	1067742	-129.98	55.93	7	6.1	7.7	-1.6	1
3308	1916-10-24	STEWART	BC	1067742	-129.98	55.93	7	6.1	7.8	-1.7	1
3309	1916-10-25	STEWART	BC	1067742	-129.98	55.93	7	6.1	6.3	-0.2	1
3310	1916-10-26	STEWART	BC	1067742	-129.98	55.93	7	6.1	7.8	-1.7	1
3311	1916-10-28	STEWART	BC	1067742	-129.98	55.93	7	3.2	7.5	-4.3	1
3312	1916-10-30	STEWART	BC	1067742	-129.98	55.93	7	3.2	4.6	-1.4	1
3313	1916-11-07	STEWART	BC	1067742	-129.98	55.93	7	3.9	4.6	-0.7	1
3314	1916-11-08	STEWART	BC	1067742	-129.98	55.93	7	6.1	7.4	-1.3	1
3315	1916-11-19	STEWART	BC	1067742	-129.98	55.93	7	0.4	1.2	-0.8	1
3316	1916-11-24	STEWART	BC	1067742	-129.98	55.93	7	-1.7	-1.5	-0.2	1
3317	1916-11-26	STEWART	BC	1067742	-129.98	55.93	7	0.8	1.1	-0.3	1
3318	1916-11-30	STEWART	BC	1067742	-129.98	55.93	7	2.3	2.7	-0.4	1
3319	1916-12-25	STEWART	BC	1067742	-129.98	55.93	7	-12.9	-12.2	-0.7	1
3320	1916-12-27	STEWART	BC	1067742	-129.98	55.93	7	-17.4	-17.1	-0.3	1
3321	1916-12-28	STEWART	BC	1067742	-129.98	55.93	7	-10.6	-10.3	-0.3	1
3322	1916-12-29	STEWART	BC	1067742	-129.98	55.93	7	-5.9	-4.1	-1.8	1
3323	1917-01-01	STEWART	BC	1067742	-129.98	55.93	7	-5.2	-4.7	-0.5	1
3324	1917-01-02	STEWART	BC	1067742	-129.98	55.93	7	-3.2	-1.8	-1.4	1
3325	1917-01-03	STEWART	BC	1067742	-129.98	55.93	7	-1.7	-1.5	-0.2	1
3326	1917-01-07	STEWART	BC	1067742	-129.98	55.93	7	0.8	2.5	-1.7	1
3327	1917-01-08	STEWART	BC	1067742	-129.98	55.93	7	1.7	4.2	-2.5	1
3328	1917-02-02	STEWART	BC	1067742	-129.98	55.93	7	-19	-16.5	-2.5	1
3329	1917-02-03	STEWART	BC	1067742	-129.98	55.93	7	-17.9	-17.1	-0.8	1
3330	1917-02-04	STEWART	BC	1067742	-129.98	55.93	7	-11.1	-9.8	-1.3	1
3331	1917-02-15	STEWART	BC	1067742	-129.98	55.93	7	2.3	2.9	-0.6	1

3332	1917-02-20	STEWART	BC	1067742	-129.98	55.93	7	-9.5	-7.8	-1.7	1
3333	1917-02-21	STEWART	BC	1067742	-129.98	55.93	7	-9.5	-9.4	-0.1	1
3334	1917-03-18	STEWART	BC	1067742	-129.98	55.93	7	4	4.5	-0.5	1
3335	1917-06-18	STEWART	BC	1067742	-129.98	55.93	7	11.1	12	-0.9	1
3336	1917-07-04	STEWART	BC	1067742	-129.98	55.93	7	11.6	12.6	-1	1
3337	1917-08-19	STEWART	BC	1067742	-129.98	55.93	7	11.9	13.1	-1.2	1
3338	1917-08-20	STEWART	BC	1067742	-129.98	55.93	7	11.6	12.6	-1	1
3339	1917-10-22	STEWART	BC	1067742	-129.98	55.93	7	7	7.1	-0.1	1
3340	1917-10-23	STEWART	BC	1067742	-129.98	55.93	7	6.5	7.5	-1	1
3341	1917-10-25	STEWART	BC	1067742	-129.98	55.93	7	7.4	7.8	-0.4	1
3342	1917-10-26	STEWART	BC	1067742	-129.98	55.93	7	7	7.4	-0.4	1
3343	1917-10-29	STEWART	BC	1067742	-129.98	55.93	7	6.1	6.3	-0.2	1
3344	1917-10-31	STEWART	BC	1067742	-129.98	55.93	7	6.1	7.8	-1.7	1
3345	1917-11-05	STEWART	BC	1067742	-129.98	55.93	7	6.1	7.1	-1	1
3346	1917-11-06	STEWART	BC	1067742	-129.98	55.93	7	7.3	7.4	-0.1	1
3347	1917-11-11	STEWART	BC	1067742	-129.98	55.93	7	6.5	7.1	-0.6	1
3348	1918-11-29	STEWART	BC	1067742	-129.98	55.93	7	0.8	0.9	-0.1	1
3349	1918-12-17	STEWART	BC	1067742	-129.98	55.93	7	0.4	0.8	-0.4	1
3350	1918-12-18	STEWART	BC	1067742	-129.98	55.93	7	0.8	0.9	-0.1	1
3351	1919-01-05	STEWART	BC	1067742	-129.98	55.93	7	0.4	0.8	-0.4	1
3352	1919-01-06	STEWART	BC	1067742	-129.98	55.93	7	0.8	2.8	-2	1
3353	1919-01-09	STEWART	BC	1067742	-129.98	55.93	7	0.4	0.8	-0.4	1
3354	1919-01-26	STEWART	BC	1067742	-129.98	55.93	7	-1.7	-1.5	-0.2	1
3355	1919-01-29	STEWART	BC	1067742	-129.98	55.93	7	-2.4	-1.5	-0.9	1
3356	1919-01-30	STEWART	BC	1067742	-129.98	55.93	7	-2.4	-1.5	-0.9	1
3357	1919-02-04	STEWART	BC	1067742	-129.98	55.93	7	-4.5	-4.2	-0.3	1
3358	1919-11-18	STEWART	BC	1067742	-129.98	55.93	7	3.1	3.3	-0.2	1
3359	1919-11-21	STEWART	BC	1067742	-129.98	55.93	7	3.1	3.3	-0.2	1
3360	1919-12-04	STEWART	BC	1067742	-129.98	55.93	7	-7.7	-6.9	-0.8	1
3361	1919-12-13	STEWART	BC	1067742	-129.98	55.93	7	-9.5	-8.3	-1.2	1
3362	1920-01-01	STEWART	BC	1067742	-129.98	55.93	7	1.7	2.6	-0.9	1
3363	1920-01-02	STEWART	BC	1067742	-129.98	55.93	7	1.7	4.9	-3.2	1
3364	1920-01-03	STEWART	BC	1067742	-129.98	55.93	7	1.7	2.5	-0.8	1
3365	1920-01-06	STEWART	BC	1067742	-129.98	55.93	7	-2.5	-1.7	-0.8	1

3366	1920-01-08	STEWART	BC	1067742	-129.98	55.93	7	1.2	2.3	-1.1	1
3367	1920-01-09	STEWART	BC	1067742	-129.98	55.93	7	0.4	1.4	-1	1
3368	1920-01-10	STEWART	BC	1067742	-129.98	55.93	7	-2.5	-1.5	-1	1
3369	1920-01-29	STEWART	BC	1067742	-129.98	55.93	7	-7.7	-6.9	-0.8	1
3370	1920-01-30	STEWART	BC	1067742	-129.98	55.93	7	-6.5	-5.8	-0.7	1
3371	1920-01-31	STEWART	BC	1067742	-129.98	55.93	7	-7.7	-7.2	-0.5	1
3372	1920-03-06	STEWART	BC	1067742	-129.98	55.93	7	-6.5	-3.7	-2.8	1
3373	1920-08-06	STEWART	BC	1067742	-129.98	55.93	7	13.9	14.3	-0.4	1
3374	1920-11-28	STEWART	BC	1067742	-129.98	55.93	7	2.4	3.2	-0.8	1
3375	1920-12-07	STEWART	BC	1067742	-129.98	55.93	7	2.4	3.1	-0.7	1
3376	1920-12-24	STEWART	BC	1067742	-129.98	55.93	7	-8.9	-7.9	-1	1
3377	1921-01-05	STEWART	BC	1067742	-129.98	55.93	7	-7.2	-5.9	-1.3	1
3378	1921-01-06	STEWART	BC	1067742	-129.98	55.93	7	-6.5	-4.1	-2.4	1
3379	1921-01-07	STEWART	BC	1067742	-129.98	55.93	7	-4	-2.7	-1.3	1
3380	1921-01-19	STEWART	BC	1067742	-129.98	55.93	7	-8.4	-7.6	-0.8	1
3381	1921-01-21	STEWART	BC	1067742	-129.98	55.93	7	-7.7	-7.6	-0.1	1
3382	1921-03-28	STEWART	BC	1067742	-129.98	55.93	7	4.7	7.6	-2.9	1
3383	1921-03-29	STEWART	BC	1067742	-129.98	55.93	7	4.7	7.7	-3	1
3384	1921-03-30	STEWART	BC	1067742	-129.98	55.93	7	5.4	7.1	-1.7	1
3385	1921-03-31	STEWART	BC	1067742	-129.98	55.93	7	3.2	4.6	-1.4	1
3386	1921-04-02	STEWART	BC	1067742	-129.98	55.93	7	3.2	7.1	-3.9	1
3387	1921-04-03	STEWART	BC	1067742	-129.98	55.93	7	5.4	6.1	-0.7	1
3388	1921-04-04	STEWART	BC	1067742	-129.98	55.93	7	6.5	7.5	-1	1
3389	1921-04-05	STEWART	BC	1067742	-129.98	55.93	7	5.4	7.1	-1.7	1
3390	1921-08-29	STEWART	BC	1067742	-129.98	55.93	7	13.4	14.3	-0.9	1
3391	1921-09-30	STEWART	BC	1067742	-129.98	55.93	7	7.8	7.9	-0.1	1
3392	1921-10-24	STEWART	BC	1067742	-129.98	55.93	7	4.7	4.9	-0.2	1
3393	1921-10-26	STEWART	BC	1067742	-129.98	55.93	7	4.7	5.8	-1.1	1
3394	1921-10-28	STEWART	BC	1067742	-129.98	55.93	7	4.7	5.8	-1.1	1
3395	1921-11-01	STEWART	BC	1067742	-129.98	55.93	7	3	4.8	-1.8	1
3396	1921-11-02	STEWART	BC	1067742	-129.98	55.93	7	3.9	5	-1.1	1
3397	1921-11-03	STEWART	BC	1067742	-129.98	55.93	7	3.9	7.6	-3.7	1
3398	1921-11-04	STEWART	BC	1067742	-129.98	55.93	7	4.7	7.6	-2.9	1
3399	1921-11-05	STEWART	BC	1067742	-129.98	55.93	7	4.7	7.4	-2.7	1

3400	1921-11-08	STEWART	BC	1067742	-129.98	55.93	7	3.9	5.8	-1.9	1
3401	1921-11-09	STEWART	BC	1067742	-129.98	55.93	7	3	7	-4	1
3402	1921-11-10	STEWART	BC	1067742	-129.98	55.93	7	2.4	4.4	-2	1
3403	1921-11-11	STEWART	BC	1067742	-129.98	55.93	7	2.4	4.4	-2	1
3404	1921-11-18	STEWART	BC	1067742	-129.98	55.93	7	-8.4	-6.9	-1.5	1
3405	1921-11-19	STEWART	BC	1067742	-129.98	55.93	7	-11.1	-7	-4.1	1
3406	1921-11-30	STEWART	BC	1067742	-129.98	55.93	7	3	4.2	-1.2	1
3407	1921-12-05	STEWART	BC	1067742	-129.98	55.93	7	2.4	3.1	-0.7	1
3408	1921-12-06	STEWART	BC	1067742	-129.98	55.93	7	2.4	3.1	-0.7	1
3409	1921-12-07	STEWART	BC	1067742	-129.98	55.93	7	3.9	5.8	-1.9	1
3410	1921-12-08	STEWART	BC	1067742	-129.98	55.93	7	3	7.1	-4.1	1
3411	1921-12-09	STEWART	BC	1067742	-129.98	55.93	7	4.8	5.8	-1	1
3412	1921-12-10	STEWART	BC	1067742	-129.98	55.93	7	1.7	5.8	-4.1	1
3413	1921-12-11	STEWART	BC	1067742	-129.98	55.93	7	1.3	4.3	-3	1
3414	1921-12-14	STEWART	BC	1067742	-129.98	55.93	7	-0.2	-0.1	-0.1	1
3415	1921-12-17	STEWART	BC	1067742	-129.98	55.93	7	-6.5	-5.5	-1	1
3416	1921-12-24	STEWART	BC	1067742	-129.98	55.93	7	-8.4	-5.9	-2.5	1
3417	1921-12-25	STEWART	BC	1067742	-129.98	55.93	7	-9.5	-6.1	-3.4	1
3418	1921-12-26	STEWART	BC	1067742	-129.98	55.93	7	-8.4	-5.8	-2.6	1
3419	1921-12-27	STEWART	BC	1067742	-129.98	55.93	7	-7.2	-7	-0.2	1
3420	1921-12-29	STEWART	BC	1067742	-129.98	55.93	7	-8.4	-7.9	-0.5	1
3421	1921-12-31	STEWART	BC	1067742	-129.98	55.93	7	-7.7	-5.8	-1.9	1
3422	1922-01-02	STEWART	BC	1067742	-129.98	55.93	7	-3.2	-3.1	-0.1	1
3423	1922-01-04	STEWART	BC	1067742	-129.98	55.93	7	-2.5	-2.1	-0.4	1
3424	1922-01-05	STEWART	BC	1067742	-129.98	55.93	7	-3.2	-1.8	-1.4	1
3425	1922-01-06	STEWART	BC	1067742	-129.98	55.93	7	-3.2	-2.1	-1.1	1
3426	1922-01-09	STEWART	BC	1067742	-129.98	55.93	7	-2.4	-1.7	-0.7	1
3427	1922-01-10	STEWART	BC	1067742	-129.98	55.93	7	-3.2	-1.8	-1.4	1
3428	1922-01-11	STEWART	BC	1067742	-129.98	55.93	7	-2.4	-1.5	-0.9	1
3429	1922-01-21	STEWART	BC	1067742	-129.98	55.93	7	-7.7	-7.4	-0.3	1
3430	1922-01-22	STEWART	BC	1067742	-129.98	55.93	7	-6.5	-5.5	-1	1
3431	1922-01-23	STEWART	BC	1067742	-129.98	55.93	7	-7.2	-5.5	-1.7	1
3432	1922-01-26	STEWART	BC	1067742	-129.98	55.93	7	-1.6	-1.1	-0.5	1
3433	1922-02-02	STEWART	BC	1067742	-129.98	55.93	7	-7.7	-7.4	-0.3	1

3434	1922-12-20	STEWART	BC	1067742	-129.98	55.93	7	-7.7	-7.5	-0.2	1
3435	1922-12-21	STEWART	BC	1067742	-129.98	55.93	7	-8.4	-7.6	-0.8	1
3436	1922-12-22	STEWART	BC	1067742	-129.98	55.93	7	-7.2	-7	-0.2	1
3437	1922-12-23	STEWART	BC	1067742	-129.98	55.93	7	-6.5	-5.9	-0.6	1
3438	1922-12-25	STEWART	BC	1067742	-129.98	55.93	7	-6.5	-6.2	-0.3	1
3439	1922-12-26	STEWART	BC	1067742	-129.98	55.93	7	-6.5	-6.2	-0.3	1
3440	1923-01-03	STEWART	BC	1067742	-129.98	55.93	7	-8.4	-7.8	-0.6	1
3441	1923-01-04	STEWART	BC	1067742	-129.98	55.93	7	-7.7	-7.6	-0.1	1
3442	1923-01-05	STEWART	BC	1067742	-129.98	55.93	7	-8.4	-7	-1.4	1
3443	1923-01-31	STEWART	BC	1067742	-129.98	55.93	7	-8.9	-7.6	-1.3	1
3444	1923-12-03	STEWART	BC	1067742	-129.98	55.93	7	3.9	4.1	-0.2	1
3445	1924-02-28	STEWART	BC	1067742	-129.98	55.93	7	6.4	7	-0.6	1
3446	1927-09-24	STEWART	BC	1067742	-129.98	55.93	7	9.5	9.7	-0.2	1
3447	1927-12-19	STEWART	BC	1067742	-129.98	55.93	7	-4.5	-3.8	-0.7	1
3448	1927-12-29	STEWART	BC	1067742	-129.98	55.93	7	-13.5	-13.4	-0.1	1
3449	1928-01-02	STEWART	BC	1067742	-129.98	55.93	7	-11.8	-11.1	-0.7	1
3450	1928-01-21	STEWART	BC	1067742	-129.98	55.93	7	-5.8	-5.2	-0.6	1
3451	1928-03-01	STEWART	BC	1067742	-129.98	55.93	7	-11.1	-10	-1.1	1
3452	1931-11-18	STEWART	BC	1067742	-129.98	55.93	7	-7.2	-5.7	-1.5	1
3453	1931-12-08	STEWART	BC	1067742	-129.98	55.93	7	-7.7	-5.7	-2	1
3454	1932-01-14	STEWART	BC	1067742	-129.98	55.93	7	-9.5	-8.9	-0.6	1
3455	1932-01-16	STEWART	BC	1067742	-129.98	55.93	7	-6.5	-5.7	-0.8	1
3456	1932-01-28	STEWART	BC	1067742	-129.98	55.93	7	-14	-13.9	-0.1	1
3457	1932-02-20	STEWART	BC	1067742	-129.98	55.93	7	-7.2	-6.2	-1	1
3458	1932-02-21	STEWART	BC	1067742	-129.98	55.93	7	-5.8	-5	-0.8	1
3459	1932-07-21	STEWART	BC	1067742	-129.98	55.93	7	13.4	14.3	-0.9	1
3460	1932-11-14	STEWART	BC	1067742	-129.98	55.93	7	-5.2	-5.1	-0.1	1
3461	1932-11-15	STEWART	BC	1067742	-129.98	55.93	7	-6.5	-5.8	-0.7	1
3462	1932-12-18	STEWART	BC	1067742	-129.98	55.93	7	-7.2	-5.7	-1.5	1
3463	1933-01-03	STEWART	BC	1067742	-129.98	55.93	7	-8.4	-6.7	-1.7	1
3464	1933-01-16	STEWART	BC	1067742	-129.98	55.93	7	-8.4	-7.8	-0.6	1
3465	1933-06-06	STEWART	BC	1067742	-129.98	55.93	7	9.5	10.5	-1	1
3466	1933-12-15	STEWART	BC	1067742	-129.98	55.93	7	-9.5	-8.9	-0.6	1
3467	1934-01-01	STEWART	BC	1067742	-129.98	55.93	7	-18.5	-18.4	-0.1	1

3468	1934-01-24	STEWART	BC	1067742	-129.98	55.93	7	-7.2	-6.7	-0.5	1
3469	1934-12-28	STEWART	BC	1067742	-129.98	55.93	7	-12.4	-10	-2.4	1
3470	1934-12-30	STEWART	BC	1067742	-129.98	55.93	7	-11.1	-10	-1.1	1
3471	1935-01-03	STEWART	BC	1067742	-129.98	55.93	7	-5.2	-4.9	-0.3	1
3472	1935-01-04	STEWART	BC	1067742	-129.98	55.93	7	-4.5	-4.4	-0.1	1
3473	1935-01-05	STEWART	BC	1067742	-129.98	55.93	7	-5.2	-4.9	-0.3	1
3474	1935-01-18	STEWART	BC	1067742	-129.98	55.93	7	-16.2	-15.6	-0.6	1
3475	1935-01-20	STEWART	BC	1067742	-129.98	55.93	7	-11.1	-10	-1.1	1
3476	1936-01-17	STEWART	BC	1067742	-129.98	55.93	7	-12.4	-10.6	-1.8	1
3477	1936-01-18	STEWART	BC	1067742	-129.98	55.93	7	-8.3	-6.8	-1.5	1
3478	1936-02-06	STEWART	BC	1067742	-129.98	55.93	7	-18.5	-16.7	-1.8	1
3479	1936-02-14	STEWART	BC	1067742	-129.98	55.93	7	-15.1	-13.9	-1.2	1
3480	1936-12-05	STEWART	BC	1067742	-129.98	55.93	7	-10	-8.9	-1.1	1
3481	1937-02-01	STEWART	BC	1067742	-129.98	55.93	7	-11.2	-9.5	-1.7	1
3482	1937-02-02	STEWART	BC	1067742	-129.98	55.93	7	-11.2	-11.1	-0.1	1
3483	1937-02-08	STEWART	BC	1067742	-129.98	55.93	7	-6.5	-5.8	-0.7	1
3484	1937-09-11	STEWART	BC	1067742	-129.98	55.93	7	10	10.2	-0.2	1
3485	1937-12-10	STEWART	BC	1067742	-129.98	55.93	7	-5.8	-4.9	-0.9	1
3486	1938-02-08	STEWART	BC	1067742	-129.98	55.93	7	-8.9	-6.7	-2.2	1
3487	1938-02-17	STEWART	BC	1067742	-129.98	55.93	7	-5.2	-5.1	-0.1	1
3488	1938-12-29	STEWART	BC	1067742	-129.98	55.93	7	-13.5	-13.4	-0.1	1
3489	1939-02-07	STEWART	BC	1067742	-129.98	55.93	7	-12.4	-12.2	-0.2	1
3490	1940-02-27	STEWART	BC	1067742	-129.98	55.93	7	-6.5	-6.2	-0.3	1
3491	1941-01-02	STEWART	BC	1067742	-129.98	55.93	7	-5.9	-5.3	-0.6	1
3492	1942-10-17	STEWART	BC	1067742	-129.98	55.93	7	6.5	7	-0.5	1
3493	1942-11-24	STEWART	BC	1067742	-129.98	55.93	7	-4.5	-4.3	-0.2	1
3494	1942-12-09	STEWART	BC	1067742	-129.98	55.93	7	-8.4	-7.2	-1.2	1
3495	1942-12-19	STEWART	BC	1067742	-129.98	55.93	7	-4.6	-4.3	-0.3	1
3496	1942-12-21	STEWART	BC	1067742	-129.98	55.93	7	-7.2	-5	-2.2	1
3497	1942-12-22	STEWART	BC	1067742	-129.98	55.93	7	-5.8	-5	-0.8	1
3498	1942-12-23	STEWART	BC	1067742	-129.98	55.93	7	-5.3	-4.2	-1.1	1
3499	1942-12-25	STEWART	BC	1067742	-129.98	55.93	7	-7.2	-5.8	-1.4	1
3500	1942-12-31	STEWART	BC	1067742	-129.98	55.93	7	-12.9	-11.1	-1.8	1
3501	1943-01-02	STEWART	BC	1067742	-129.98	55.93	7	-9.5	-6.2	-3.3	1

3502	1943-01-03	STEWART	BC	1067742	-129.98	55.93	7	-7.2	-6.7	-0.5	1
3503	1943-01-23	STEWART	BC	1067742	-129.98	55.93	7	-17.4	-17.2	-0.2	1
3504	1943-01-24	STEWART	BC	1067742	-129.98	55.93	7	-16.8	-16.7	-0.1	1
3505	1943-01-31	STEWART	BC	1067742	-129.98	55.93	7	-5.8	-5.1	-0.7	1
3506	1943-02-09	STEWART	BC	1067742	-129.98	55.93	7	-9.5	-6.7	-2.8	1
3507	1943-02-10	STEWART	BC	1067742	-129.98	55.93	7	-5.8	-5.2	-0.6	1
3508	1943-09-28	STEWART	BC	1067742	-129.98	55.93	7	7.8	7.9	-0.1	1
3509	1944-01-02	STEWART	BC	1067742	-129.98	55.93	7	-8.9	-5.7	-3.2	1
3510	1944-01-04	STEWART	BC	1067742	-129.98	55.93	7	-5.9	-4.4	-1.5	1
3511	1944-01-08	STEWART	BC	1067742	-129.98	55.93	7	-5.9	-4.4	-1.5	1
3512	1944-01-30	STEWART	BC	1067742	-129.98	55.93	7	1.2	1.4	-0.2	1
3513	1944-03-01	STEWART	BC	1067742	-129.98	55.93	7	-6.5	-5.4	-1.1	1
3514	1944-05-19	STEWART	BC	1067742	-129.98	55.93	7	10.1	10.4	-0.3	1
3515	1944-09-18	STEWART	BC	1067742	-129.98	55.93	7	8.6	9.6	-1	1
3516	1944-12-31	STEWART	BC	1067742	-129.98	55.93	7	-12.9	-11.1	-1.8	1
3517	1945-02-06	STEWART	BC	1067742	-129.98	55.93	7	0.8	1.3	-0.5	1
3518	1945-02-12	STEWART	BC	1067742	-129.98	55.93	7	-4	-3.9	-0.1	1
3519	1945-02-13	STEWART	BC	1067742	-129.98	55.93	7	-9.5	-7.2	-2.3	1
3520	1945-02-14	STEWART	BC	1067742	-129.98	55.93	7	-14.6	-11.7	-2.9	1
3521	1945-02-15	STEWART	BC	1067742	-129.98	55.93	7	-11.2	-8.9	-2.3	1
3522	1945-02-16	STEWART	BC	1067742	-129.98	55.93	7	-12.9	-10.6	-2.3	1
3523	1945-02-18	STEWART	BC	1067742	-129.98	55.93	7	-4	-3.9	-0.1	1
3524	1945-09-23	STEWART	BC	1067742	-129.98	55.93	7	10	10.4	-0.4	1
3525	1945-11-19	STEWART	BC	1067742	-129.98	55.93	7	-4.5	-4.3	-0.2	1
3526	1945-12-18	STEWART	BC	1067742	-129.98	55.93	7	-7.7	-5.9	-1.8	1
3527	1946-01-25	STEWART	BC	1067742	-129.98	55.93	7	-7.2	-6.1	-1.1	1
3528	1946-12-13	STEWART	BC	1067742	-129.98	55.93	7	-8.9	-8.7	-0.2	1
3529	1946-12-16	STEWART	BC	1067742	-129.98	55.93	7	-5.9	-5.5	-0.4	1
3530	1946-12-28	STEWART	BC	1067742	-129.98	55.93	7	-8.9	-8.1	-0.8	1
3531	1946-12-29	STEWART	BC	1067742	-129.98	55.93	7	-8.9	-8.1	-0.8	1
3532	1947-01-13	STEWART	BC	1067742	-129.98	55.93	7	-11.2	-11	-0.2	1
3533	1947-01-14	STEWART	BC	1067742	-129.98	55.93	7	-7.2	-7	-0.2	1
3534	1947-01-15	STEWART	BC	1067742	-129.98	55.93	7	-10	-8.7	-1.3	1
3535	1947-02-02	STEWART	BC	1067742	-129.98	55.93	7	-17.4	-14.6	-2.8	1

3536	1947-02-03	STEWART	BC	1067742	-129.98	55.93	7	-10	-8.1	-1.9	1
3537	1947-02-04	STEWART	BC	1067742	-129.98	55.93	7	-9.5	-7	-2.5	1
3538	1947-02-05	STEWART	BC	1067742	-129.98	55.93	7	-8.4	-6.7	-1.7	1
3539	1947-02-06	STEWART	BC	1067742	-129.98	55.93	7	-10.6	-10.5	-0.1	1
3540	1948-12-05	STEWART	BC	1067742	-129.98	55.93	7	-7.2	-5.6	-1.6	1
3541	1948-12-17	STEWART	BC	1067742	-129.98	55.93	7	-14	-13.4	-0.6	1
3542	1949-01-03	STEWART	BC	1067742	-129.98	55.93	7	-7.2	-5.9	-1.3	1
3543	1949-01-10	STEWART	BC	1067742	-129.98	55.93	7	-7.2	-6.5	-0.7	1
3544	1949-01-24	STEWART	BC	1067742	-129.98	55.93	7	-8.4	-8.1	-0.3	1
3545	1949-12-19	STEWART	BC	1067742	-129.98	55.93	7	-11.1	-11	-0.1	1
3546	1949-12-30	STEWART	BC	1067742	-129.98	55.93	7	-11.2	-11	-0.2	1
3547	1950-11-14	STEWART	BC	1067742	-129.98	55.93	7	-8.9	-8.7	-0.2	1
3548	1951-02-02	STEWART	BC	1067742	-129.98	55.93	7	-8.9	-8.7	-0.2	1
3549	1951-02-07	STEWART	BC	1067742	-129.98	55.93	7	-8.9	-8.7	-0.2	1
3550	1951-03-12	STEWART	BC	1067742	-129.98	55.93	7	-6.5	-5.8	-0.7	1
3551	1951-12-23	STEWART	BC	1067742	-129.98	55.93	7	-7.2	-7	-0.2	1
3552	1951-12-24	STEWART	BC	1067742	-129.98	55.93	7	-7.2	-6.6	-0.6	1
3553	1952-01-22	STEWART	BC	1067742	-129.98	55.93	7	-14	-8.7	-5.3	1
3554	1952-01-23	STEWART	BC	1067742	-129.98	55.93	7	-10.6	-8.1	-2.5	1
3555	1952-01-24	STEWART	BC	1067742	-129.98	55.93	7	-10	-6.6	-3.4	1
3556	1952-01-25	STEWART	BC	1067742	-129.98	55.93	7	-7.7	-5.4	-2.3	1
3557	1952-01-26	STEWART	BC	1067742	-129.98	55.93	7	-3.2	-2.4	-0.8	1
3558	1953-01-09	STEWART	BC	1067742	-129.98	55.93	7	-23.5	-21.2	-2.3	1
3559	1953-01-13	STEWART	BC	1067742	-129.98	55.93	7	-19.6	-17.9	-1.7	1
3560	1953-01-14	STEWART	BC	1067742	-129.98	55.93	7	-21.2	-20.7	-0.5	1
3561	1953-01-19	STEWART	BC	1067742	-129.98	55.93	7	-9.5	-9.3	-0.2	1
3562	1954-01-24	STEWART	BC	1067742	-129.98	55.93	7	-11.8	-10.5	-1.3	1
3563	1954-01-25	STEWART	BC	1067742	-129.98	55.93	7	-12.9	-12.8	-0.1	1
3564	1954-01-26	STEWART	BC	1067742	-129.98	55.93	7	-11.8	-11.1	-0.7	1
3565	1954-01-27	STEWART	BC	1067742	-129.98	55.93	7	-13.5	-12.8	-0.7	1
3566	1954-10-08	STEWART	BC	1067742	-129.98	55.93	7	7.3	7.8	-0.5	1
3567	1954-10-18	STEWART	BC	1067742	-129.98	55.93	7	8.2	8.4	-0.2	1
3568	1954-12-30	STEWART	BC	1067742	-129.98	55.93	7	-11.1	-9.9	-1.2	1
3569	1954-12-31	STEWART	BC	1067742	-129.98	55.93	7	-10.6	-8.7	-1.9	1

3570	1955-01-16	STEWART	BC	1067742	-129.98	55.93	7	-6.5	-5.6	-0.9	1
3571	1955-06-24	STEWART	BC	1067742	-129.98	55.93	7	9.5	9.6	-0.1	1
3572	1955-08-16	STEWART	BC	1067742	-129.98	55.93	7	9.5	9.8	-0.3	1
3573	1955-12-17	STEWART	BC	1067742	-129.98	55.93	7	-11.8	-11.7	-0.1	1
3574	1955-12-18	STEWART	BC	1067742	-129.98	55.93	7	-12.4	-11.7	-0.7	1
3575	1955-12-22	STEWART	BC	1067742	-129.98	55.93	7	-11.1	-11	-0.1	1
3576	1955-12-27	STEWART	BC	1067742	-129.98	55.93	7	-9.5	-8.7	-0.8	1
3577	1956-01-30	STEWART	BC	1067742	-129.98	55.93	7	-12.9	-12.2	-0.7	1
3578	1956-01-31	STEWART	BC	1067742	-129.98	55.93	7	-8.9	-8.7	-0.2	1
3579	1956-02-15	STEWART	BC	1067742	-129.98	55.93	7	-17.4	-16.8	-0.6	1
3580	1956-12-03	STEWART	BC	1067742	-129.98	55.93	7	-8.9	-8.7	-0.2	1
3581	1956-12-08	STEWART	BC	1067742	-129.98	55.93	7	-7.7	-6.6	-1.1	1
3582	1956-12-12	STEWART	BC	1067742	-129.98	55.93	7	-7.7	-7	-0.7	1
3583	1956-12-13	STEWART	BC	1067742	-129.98	55.93	7	-7.7	-6.2	-1.5	1
3584	1958-11-04	STEWART	BC	1067742	-129.98	55.93	7	3	3.3	-0.3	1
3585	1959-01-02	STEWART	BC	1067742	-129.98	55.93	7	-19	-17.3	-1.7	1
3586	1961-09-18	STEWART	BC	1067742	-129.98	55.93	7	8.2	8.4	-0.2	1
3587	1961-09-20	STEWART	BC	1067742	-129.98	55.93	7	8.2	8.4	-0.2	1
3588	1961-09-21	STEWART	BC	1067742	-129.98	55.93	7	8.6	9	-0.4	1
3589	1961-10-04	STEWART	BC	1067742	-129.98	55.93	7	6.5	7.3	-0.8	1
3590	1961-10-11	STEWART	BC	1067742	-129.98	55.93	7	7.4	7.8	-0.4	1
3591	1961-12-19	STEWART	BC	1067742	-129.98	55.93	7	-10.6	-9.8	-0.8	1
3592	1962-10-07	STEWART	BC	1067742	-129.98	55.93	7	3.8	4.1	-0.3	1
3593	1962-12-30	STEWART	BC	1067742	-129.98	55.93	7	-7.2	-6.1	-1.1	1
3594	1962-12-31	STEWART	BC	1067742	-129.98	55.93	7	-11.2	-10.5	-0.7	1
3595	1965-10-03	STEWART	BC	1067742	-129.98	55.93	7	9	9.5	-0.5	1
3596	1965-10-08	STEWART	BC	1067742	-129.98	55.93	7	7	7.8	-0.8	1
3597	1965-10-11	STEWART	BC	1067742	-129.98	55.93	7	7	7.8	-0.8	1
3598	1965-10-22	STEWART	BC	1067742	-129.98	55.93	7	6.9	7.3	-0.4	1
3599	1965-10-28	STEWART	BC	1067742	-129.98	55.93	7	7.3	8.4	-1.1	1
3600	1966-01-02	STEWART	BC	1067742	-129.98	55.93	7	-12.9	-12.8	-0.1	1
3601	1966-01-20	STEWART	BC	1067742	-129.98	55.93	7	-6.5	-6.1	-0.4	1
3602	1966-01-27	STEWART	BC	1067742	-129.98	55.93	7	-8.4	-7	-1.4	1
3603	1966-01-28	STEWART	BC	1067742	-129.98	55.93	7	-7.7	-7.6	-0.1	1

3604	1966-09-03	STEWART	BC	1067742	-129.98	55.93	7	8.2	9	-0.8	1
3605	1966-09-29	STEWART	BC	1067742	-129.98	55.93	7	8.7	9	-0.3	1
3606	1966-10-05	STEWART	BC	1067742	-129.98	55.93	7	9.1	9.6	-0.5	1
3607	1966-12-06	STEWART	BC	1067742	-129.98	55.93	7	-8.4	-8.1	-0.3	1
3608	2006-01-21	CHELSEA	QUE	7031360	-75.78	45.52	113	-7	-6	-1	1
3609	2006-01-25	CHELSEA	QUE	7031360	-75.78	45.52	113	-7	-4	-3	1
3610	1913-03-28	LES CEDRES	QUE	7014290	-74.05	45.3	47	-4.5	-3.4	-1.1	1
3611	1914-12-14	LES CEDRES	QUE	7014290	-74.05	45.3	47	-10.3	-2.8	-7.5	1
3612	1920-12-27	LES CEDRES	QUE	7014290	-74.05	45.3	47	-9.6	-9.5	-0.1	1
3613	1921-12-24	LES CEDRES	QUE	7014290	-74.05	45.3	47	-13.1	-10	-3.1	1
3614	1965-02-12	LES CEDRES	QUE	7014290	-74.05	45.3	47	-10.3	-5.1	-5.2	1
3615	1965-02-18	LES CEDRES	QUE	7014290	-74.05	45.3	47	-14.2	-10	-4.2	1
3616	1971-12-21	LES CEDRES	QUE	7014290	-74.05	45.3	47	-12.5	-7.5	-5	1
3617	2006-12-26	LES CEDRES	QUE	7014290	-74.05	45.3	47	-5.5	0.5	-6	1
3618	2010-11-23	LES CEDRES	QUE	7014290	-74.05	45.3	47	1	1.5	-0.5	1
3619	1917-11-13	GLACIER	BC	1173191	-117.52	51.3	1330	-1.3	-0.5	-0.8	1
3620	1933-11-17	GLACIER	BC	1173191	-117.52	51.3	1330	-0.5	-0.2	-0.3	1
3621	1935-11-28	GLACIER	BC	1173191	-117.52	51.3	1330	-1.8	-1.4	-0.4	1
3622	1945-11-18	GLACIER	BC	1173191	-117.52	51.3	1330	-2.4	-2	-0.4	1
3623	1946-10-24	GLACIER	BC	1173191	-117.52	51.3	1330	-0.4	-0.2	-0.2	1
3624	1947-02-14	GLACIER	BC	1173191	-117.52	51.3	1330	-0.4	-0.2	-0.2	1
3625	1947-10-16	GLACIER	BC	1173191	-117.52	51.3	1330	0.3	0.4	-0.1	1
3626	1949-11-19	GLACIER	BC	1173191	-117.52	51.3	1330	-1.8	-1.4	-0.4	1
3627	1953-12-31	GLACIER	BC	1173191	-117.52	51.3	1330	-4.2	-3.9	-0.3	1
3628	1954-02-28	GLACIER	BC	1173191	-117.52	51.3	1330	-5	-3.9	-1.1	1
3629	1955-02-16	GLACIER	BC	1173191	-117.52	51.3	1330	-4.1	-3.4	-0.7	1
3630	1955-11-09	GLACIER	BC	1173191	-117.52	51.3	1330	-0.6	-0.2	-0.4	1
3631	1958-01-07	GLACIER	BC	1173191	-117.52	51.3	1330	-7.2	-6.5	-0.7	1
3632	1958-02-11	GLACIER	BC	1173191	-117.52	51.3	1330	-5.6	-4.4	-1.2	1
3633	1958-02-12	GLACIER	BC	1173191	-117.52	51.3	1330	-8.9	-8.4	-0.5	1
3634	1959-11-01	GLACIER	BC	1173191	-117.52	51.3	1330	0.3	0.4	-0.1	1
3635	1961-12-02	GLACIER	BC	1173191	-117.52	51.3	1330	-1.8	-1.4	-0.4	1
3636	1926-01-14	WISTARIA	BC	1085835	-126.22	53.83	861	-2.2	-1.7	-0.5	1
3637	1926-02-01	WISTARIA	BC	1085835	-126.22	53.83	861	-6.8	-6.7	-0.1	1

3638	1926-11-19	WISTARIA	BC	1085835	-126.22	53.83	861	-4	-3.9	-0.1	1
3639	1926-11-28	WISTARIA	BC	1085835	-126.22	53.83	861	-10.2	-8.3	-1.9	1
3640	1926-12-03	WISTARIA	BC	1085835	-126.22	53.83	861	-9.6	-8.9	-0.7	1
3641	1926-12-14	WISTARIA	BC	1085835	-126.22	53.83	861	-22.5	-21.1	-1.4	1
3642	1926-12-17	WISTARIA	BC	1085835	-126.22	53.83	861	-9.5	-7.8	-1.7	1
3643	1926-12-28	WISTARIA	BC	1085835	-126.22	53.83	861	-2.3	-2.2	-0.1	1
3644	1928-01-11	WISTARIA	BC	1085835	-126.22	53.83	861	-1.8	-1.1	-0.7	1
3645	1928-11-25	WISTARIA	BC	1085835	-126.22	53.83	861	-5.3	-5	-0.3	1
3646	1928-11-27	WISTARIA	BC	1085835	-126.22	53.83	861	-8	-6.7	-1.3	1
3647	1928-12-29	WISTARIA	BC	1085835	-126.22	53.83	861	-9.5	-9.4	-0.1	1
3648	1929-01-02	WISTARIA	BC	1085835	-126.22	53.83	861	-8	-6.7	-1.3	1
3649	1929-01-25	WISTARIA	BC	1085835	-126.22	53.83	861	-14.5	-13.9	-0.6	1
3650	1929-08-11	WISTARIA	BC	1085835	-126.22	53.83	861	3.9	7.2	-3.3	1
3651	1929-11-19	WISTARIA	BC	1085835	-126.22	53.83	861	-4	-3.9	-0.1	1
3652	1929-12-10	WISTARIA	BC	1085835	-126.22	53.83	861	-25.3	-24.4	-0.9	1
3653	1930-12-17	WISTARIA	BC	1085835	-126.22	53.83	861	-2.8	-2.2	-0.6	1
3654	1931-03-11	WISTARIA	BC	1085835	-126.22	53.83	861	-15.7	-15.6	-0.1	1
3655	1931-11-15	WISTARIA	BC	1085835	-126.22	53.83	861	-16.9	-16.7	-0.2	1
3656	1931-11-17	WISTARIA	BC	1085835	-126.22	53.83	861	-15.7	-15.6	-0.1	1
3657	1931-12-13	WISTARIA	BC	1085835	-126.22	53.83	861	-11.5	-11.1	-0.4	1
3658	1932-01-10	WISTARIA	BC	1085835	-126.22	53.83	861	-0.5	0.6	-1.1	1
3659	1933-10-23	WISTARIA	BC	1085835	-126.22	53.83	861	-15.7	-15	-0.7	1
3660	1933-12-20	WISTARIA	BC	1085835	-126.22	53.83	861	-26.4	-26.1	-0.3	1
3661	1934-01-01	WISTARIA	BC	1085835	-126.22	53.83	861	-25.8	-25.6	-0.2	1
3662	1935-01-17	WISTARIA	BC	1085835	-126.22	53.83	861	-29.7	-29.4	-0.3	1
3663	1936-01-15	WISTARIA	BC	1085835	-126.22	53.83	861	-16.4	-15.6	-0.8	1
3664	1939-12-26	WISTARIA	BC	1085835	-126.22	53.83	861	-8.6	-8.3	-0.3	1
3665	1940-01-09	WISTARIA	BC	1085835	-126.22	53.83	861	-12.3	-12.2	-0.1	1
3666	1940-11-07	WISTARIA	BC	1085835	-126.22	53.83	861	-16.9	-16.7	-0.2	1
3667	1940-12-12	WISTARIA	BC	1085835	-126.22	53.83	861	-13.4	-13.3	-0.1	1
3668	1940-12-17	WISTARIA	BC	1085835	-126.22	53.83	861	-13.4	-13.3	-0.1	1
3669	1940-12-30	WISTARIA	BC	1085835	-126.22	53.83	861	-11.1	-10	-1.1	1
3670	1941-01-05	WISTARIA	BC	1085835	-126.22	53.83	861	-7.3	-7.2	-0.1	1
3671	1941-01-06	WISTARIA	BC	1085835	-126.22	53.83	861	-8.6	-8.3	-0.3	1

3672	1941-01-24	WISTARIA	BC	1085835	-126.22	53.83	861	-25.8	-25	-0.8	1
3673	1941-12-28	WISTARIA	BC	1085835	-126.22	53.83	861	-21.9	-21.1	-0.8	1
3674	1944-01-09	WISTARIA	BC	1085835	-126.22	53.83	861	-8.6	-8.3	-0.3	1
3675	1945-01-30	WISTARIA	BC	1085835	-126.22	53.83	861	-12.9	-12.8	-0.1	1
3676	1945-02-02	WISTARIA	BC	1085835	-126.22	53.83	861	-8.6	-8.3	-0.3	1
3677	1945-12-26	WISTARIA	BC	1085835	-126.22	53.83	861	-9.8	-8.9	-0.9	1
3678	1949-12-28	WISTARIA	BC	1085835	-126.22	53.83	861	-24.7	-23.3	-1.4	1
3679	1949-12-30	WISTARIA	BC	1085835	-126.22	53.83	861	-26.4	-26.1	-0.3	1
3680	1950-01-08	WISTARIA	BC	1085835	-126.22	53.83	861	-21.4	-20.6	-0.8	1
3681	1950-11-15	WISTARIA	BC	1085835	-126.22	53.83	861	-15.7	-15.6	-0.1	1
3682	1950-11-20	WISTARIA	BC	1085835	-126.22	53.83	861	-17.5	-17.2	-0.3	1
3683	1951-01-02	WISTARIA	BC	1085835	-126.22	53.83	861	-9.8	-9.4	-0.4	1
3684	1951-02-04	WISTARIA	BC	1085835	-126.22	53.83	861	-13.4	-13.3	-0.1	1
3685	1951-03-04	WISTARIA	BC	1085835	-126.22	53.83	861	-25.8	-25.6	-0.2	1
3686	1951-12-14	WISTARIA	BC	1085835	-126.22	53.83	861	-20.3	-18.3	-2	1
3687	1951-12-18	WISTARIA	BC	1085835	-126.22	53.83	861	-23.1	-22.2	-0.9	1
3688	1951-12-26	WISTARIA	BC	1085835	-126.22	53.83	861	-15.2	-14.4	-0.8	1
3689	1952-01-14	WISTARIA	BC	1085835	-126.22	53.83	861	-26.9	-25.6	-1.3	1
3690	1915-12-24	MANIWAKI	QUE	7034482	-76	46.3	200	-8.8	-8.3	-0.5	1
3691	1915-12-25	MANIWAKI	QUE	7034482	-76	46.3	200	-10.7	-10	-0.7	1
3692	1916-03-09	MANIWAKI	QUE	7034482	-76	46.3	200	-13.2	-12.8	-0.4	1
3693	1916-03-10	MANIWAKI	QUE	7034482	-76	46.3	200	-12.6	-12.2	-0.4	1
3694	1917-12-22	MANIWAKI	QUE	7034482	-76	46.3	200	-8.9	-7.8	-1.1	1
3695	1918-02-02	MANIWAKI	QUE	7034482	-76	46.3	200	-11.6	-11.1	-0.5	1
3696	1919-01-29	MANIWAKI	QUE	7034482	-76	46.3	200	-7.8	-7.2	-0.6	1
3697	1919-10-07	MANIWAKI	QUE	7034482	-76	46.3	200	6	13.9	-7.9	1
3698	1919-10-16	MANIWAKI	QUE	7034482	-76	46.3	200	2.6	7.8	-5.2	1
3699	1919-10-26	MANIWAKI	QUE	7034482	-76	46.3	200	2.6	2.8	-0.2	1
3700	1919-11-21	MANIWAKI	QUE	7034482	-76	46.3	200	-6.5	-6.1	-0.4	1
3701	1919-12-20	MANIWAKI	QUE	7034482	-76	46.3	200	-13.2	-12.2	-1	1
3702	1921-02-25	MANIWAKI	QUE	7034482	-76	46.3	200	-8.3	-6.1	-2.2	1
3703	1921-06-04	MANIWAKI	QUE	7034482	-76	46.3	200	13.4	14.4	-1	1
3704	1922-01-04	MANIWAKI	QUE	7034482	-76	46.3	200	-11.6	-11.1	-0.5	1
3705	1922-03-07	MANIWAKI	QUE	7034482	-76	46.3	200	2.7	3.3	-0.6	1

3706	1922-03-20	MANIWAKI	QUE	7034482	-76	46.3	200	-0.7	0	-0.7	1
3707	1922-04-12	MANIWAKI	QUE	7034482	-76	46.3	200	5.4	5.6	-0.2	1
3708	1926-11-02	MANIWAKI	QUE	7034482	-76	46.3	200	-1.4	-0.6	-0.8	1
3709	1926-11-07	MANIWAKI	QUE	7034482	-76	46.3	200	0.8	1.1	-0.3	1
3710	1926-11-11	MANIWAKI	QUE	7034482	-76	46.3	200	-8.8	-7.8	-1	1
3711	1926-11-17	MANIWAKI	QUE	7034482	-76	46.3	200	-0.2	2.2	-2.4	1
3712	1926-11-18	MANIWAKI	QUE	7034482	-76	46.3	200	-1.4	0	-1.4	1
3713	1926-11-19	MANIWAKI	QUE	7034482	-76	46.3	200	-5.7	-0.6	-5.1	1
3714	1927-07-23	MANIWAKI	QUE	7034482	-76	46.3	200	16.1	16.7	-0.6	1
3715	1927-11-11	MANIWAKI	QUE	7034482	-76	46.3	200	-0.9	-0.6	-0.3	1
3716	1927-11-23	MANIWAKI	QUE	7034482	-76	46.3	200	-3.7	-3.3	-0.4	1
3717	1927-12-14	MANIWAKI	QUE	7034482	-76	46.3	200	-6.7	-5.6	-1.1	1
3718	1994-03-23	CAPE PARRY	NWT	2200675	-124.72	70.17	87	-28.8	-28.2	-0.6	1
3719	1994-11-14	CAPE PARRY	NWT	2200675	-124.72	70.17	87	-20.6	-17.4	-3.2	1
3720	1994-11-24	CAPE PARRY	NWT	2200675	-124.72	70.17	87	-24.1	-20.7	-3.4	1
3721	2019-11-15	CAPE PARRY	NWT	2200675	-124.72	70.17	87	-16.8	-4.4	-12.4	1
3722	1932-03-25	NATASHQUAN	QUE	7045401	-61.82	50.18	11	-3.9	-3.5	-0.4	1
3723	1936-01-24	NATASHQUAN	QUE	7045401	-61.82	50.18	11	-13.3	-10.3	-3	1
3724	2012-12-15	NATASHQUAN	QUE	7045401	-61.82	50.18	11	-11.2	-7.8	-3.4	1
3725	2012-12-27	NATASHQUAN	QUE	7045401	-61.82	50.18	11	-8.1	-3.1	-5	1
3726	2005-01-04	ST JEROME	QUE	7037400	-74.05	45.8	170	-9	-8.5	-0.5	1
3727	2005-01-17	ST JEROME	QUE	7037400	-74.05	45.8	170	-21	-19.5	-1.5	1
3728	1915-11-11	MADAWASKA	ONT	6080192	-77.98	45.5	397	7.8	7.9	-0.1	1
3729	1915-12-17	MADAWASKA	ONT	6080192	-77.98	45.5	397	0.7	0.8	-0.1	1
3730	1916-01-12	MADAWASKA	ONT	6080192	-77.98	45.5	397	-1.7	-1.2	-0.5	1
3731	1916-01-21	MADAWASKA	ONT	6080192	-77.98	45.5	397	7.3	7.4	-0.1	1
3732	1916-11-28	MADAWASKA	ONT	6080192	-77.98	45.5	397	5.7	6.2	-0.5	1
3733	1916-12-27	MADAWASKA	ONT	6080192	-77.98	45.5	397	-0.2	0.4	-0.6	1
3734	1918-02-11	MADAWASKA	ONT	6080192	-77.98	45.5	397	0.1	0.5	-0.4	1
3735	1919-03-16	MADAWASKA	ONT	6080192	-77.98	45.5	397	0.1	0.4	-0.3	1
3736	1919-12-12	MADAWASKA	ONT	6080192	-77.98	45.5	397	0.7	0.9	-0.2	1
3737	1920-03-19	MADAWASKA	ONT	6080192	-77.98	45.5	397	0.1	0.5	-0.4	1
3738	1923-12-05	MADAWASKA	ONT	6080192	-77.98	45.5	397	0.1	0.4	-0.3	1
3739	1923-12-31	MADAWASKA	ONT	6080192	-77.98	45.5	397	-13.6	-13.5	-0.1	1

3740	1925-12-20	MADAWASKA	ONT	6080192	-77.98	45.5	397	-1.4	-0.9	-0.5	1
3741	1929-11-18	MADAWASKA	ONT	6080192	-77.98	45.5	397	-0.5	0	-0.5	1
3742	2010-11-21	MADAWASKA	ONT	6080192	-77.98	45.5	397	-1.5	4.2	-5.7	1
3743	2011-12-20	MADAWASKA	ONT	6080192	-77.98	45.5	397	-2.7	-1.7	-1	1
3744	2012-12-16	MADAWASKA	ONT	6080192	-77.98	45.5	397	-0.9	0.1	-1	1
3745	2013-11-12	MADAWASKA	ONT	6080192	-77.98	45.5	397	-5.9	-4.4	-1.5	1
3746	2013-11-13	MADAWASKA	ONT	6080192	-77.98	45.5	397	-0.3	6.5	-6.8	1
3747	1982-11-14	TETE BALEINE	QUE	7041382	-59.32	50.7	8	-4	-1.5	-2.5	1
3748	1995-10-14	TETE BALEINE	QUE	7041382	-59.32	50.7	8	8.6	8.7	-0.1	1
3749	1996-05-12	TETE BALEINE	QUE	7041382	-59.32	50.7	8	0	0.1	-0.1	1
3750	1996-12-18	TETE BALEINE	QUE	7041382	-59.32	50.7	8	-1.2	-0.1	-1.1	1
3751	1997-01-07	TETE BALEINE	QUE	7041382	-59.32	50.7	8	-11.1	-3.3	-7.8	1
3752	1997-01-24	TETE BALEINE	QUE	7041382	-59.32	50.7	8	-18.1	-0.3	-17.8	1
3753	1997-12-16	TETE BALEINE	QUE	7041382	-59.32	50.7	8	-13.4	-12.1	-1.3	1
3754	1998-02-23	TETE BALEINE	QUE	7041382	-59.32	50.7	8	-7.6	0	-7.6	1
3755	1998-02-24	TETE BALEINE	QUE	7041382	-59.32	50.7	8	-2.3	-0.3	-2	1
3756	1978-12-16	ST JOHN'S	NFLD	8403505	-52.75	47.62	141	0	5.8	-5.8	1
3757	1987-06-01	ST JOHN'S	NFLD	8403505	-52.75	47.62	141	2.8	3.7	-0.9	1
3758	2007-10-14	LUPIN	NU	230N002	-111.23	65.77	488	-7.8	-6.9	-0.9	1
3759	2007-10-18	LUPIN	NU	230N002	-111.23	65.77	488	-4	-3.6	-0.4	1
3760	2008-12-09	LUPIN	NU	230N002	-111.23	65.77	488	-36.8	-29.2	-7.6	1
3761	2012-03-29	LUPIN	NU	230N002	-111.23	65.77	488	-9.2	-8.8	-0.4	1
3762	2014-01-18	LUPIN	NU	230N002	-111.23	65.77	488	-37.5	-34.4	-3.1	1
3763	2014-01-20	LUPIN	NU	230N002	-111.23	65.77	488	-28.5	-26.7	-1.8	1
3764	2014-01-25	LUPIN	NU	230N002	-111.23	65.77	488	-28.6	-26.4	-2.2	1
3765	2017-01-12	LUPIN	NU	230N002	-111.23	65.77	488	-34.5	-33.2	-1.3	1
3766	2017-03-12	LUPIN	NU	230N002	-111.23	65.77	488	-20.5	-18.7	-1.8	1
3767	1905-06-26	GLEICHEN	ALTA	3032801	-113.05	50.88	907	10.6	10.9	-0.3	1
3768	1908-06-27	GLEICHEN	ALTA	3032801	-113.05	50.88	907	8.3	11.5	-3.2	1
3769	1909-05-22	GLEICHEN	ALTA	3032801	-113.05	50.88	907	9.4	10.8	-1.4	1
3770	1909-11-27	GLEICHEN	ALTA	3032801	-113.05	50.88	907	1.1	6.1	-5	1
3771	1910-01-23	GLEICHEN	ALTA	3032801	-113.05	50.88	907	-3.3	-2.7	-0.6	1
3772	2008-12-20	GLEICHEN	ALTA	3032801	-113.05	50.88	907	-26.3	-23.9	-2.4	1
3773	2008-12-23	GLEICHEN	ALTA	3032801	-113.05	50.88	907	-21.3	-17.7	-3.6	1

3774	2008-12-26	GLEICHEN	ALTA	3032801	-113.05	50.88	907	-15.7	-13.7	-2	1
3775	1982-02-06	PLUM POINT	NFLD	8402958	-56.88	51.07	6	-14	-12	-2	1
3776	2007-08-09	PLUM POINT	NFLD	8402958	-56.88	51.07	6	12	13.5	-1.5	1
3777	2008-01-01	PLUM POINT	NFLD	8402958	-56.88	51.07	6	-9	-8.5	-0.5	1
3778	1915-08-17	ROCKY MTN HOUSE	ALTA	3015523	-114.92	52.43	988	18.1	19	-0.9	1
3779	1915-08-18	ROCKY MTN HOUSE	ALTA	3015523	-114.92	52.43	988	14.8	15.8	-1	1
3780	1915-09-23	ROCKY MTN HOUSE	ALTA	3015523	-114.92	52.43	988	3	4	-1	1
3781	1917-01-20	ROCKY MTN HOUSE	ALTA	3015523	-114.92	52.43	988	-23.6	-21	-2.6	1
3782	1917-01-26	ROCKY MTN HOUSE	ALTA	3015523	-114.92	52.43	988	-10.5	-5.7	-4.8	1
3783	1917-02-03	ROCKY MTN HOUSE	ALTA	3015523	-114.92	52.43	988	-28	-23.1	-4.9	1
3784	1917-02-10	ROCKY MTN HOUSE	ALTA	3015523	-114.92	52.43	988	-4.6	-1.5	-3.1	1
3785	1917-02-19	ROCKY MTN HOUSE	ALTA	3015523	-114.92	52.43	988	-28	-25.2	-2.8	1
3786	1917-05-16	ROCKY MTN HOUSE	ALTA	3015523	-114.92	52.43	988	1	4.8	-3.8	1
3787	1917-05-21	ROCKY MTN HOUSE	ALTA	3015523	-114.92	52.43	988	8.6	10.3	-1.7	1
3788	1917-05-23	ROCKY MTN HOUSE	ALTA	3015523	-114.92	52.43	988	5	13.1	-8.1	1
3789	1917-05-24	ROCKY MTN HOUSE	ALTA	3015523	-114.92	52.43	988	3.8	4.8	-1	1
3790	1917-06-19	ROCKY MTN HOUSE	ALTA	3015523	-114.92	52.43	988	8.5	10.4	-1.9	1
3791	1917-06-24	ROCKY MTN HOUSE	ALTA	3015523	-114.92	52.43	988	10.4	10.9	-0.5	1
3792	1917-12-06	ROCKY MTN HOUSE	ALTA	3015523	-114.92	52.43	988	-19.2	-18.6	-0.6	1
3793	1917-12-08	ROCKY MTN HOUSE	ALTA	3015523	-114.92	52.43	988	-20.8	-19.6	-1.2	1
3794	1917-12-11	ROCKY MTN HOUSE	ALTA	3015523	-114.92	52.43	988	-26.9	-25.6	-1.3	1
3795	1917-12-19	ROCKY MTN HOUSE	ALTA	3015523	-114.92	52.43	988	-8.5	-3.7	-4.8	1
3796	1917-12-25	ROCKY MTN HOUSE	ALTA	3015523	-114.92	52.43	988	-26.3	-25.2	-1.1	1
3797	1917-12-27	ROCKY MTN HOUSE	ALTA	3015523	-114.92	52.43	988	-26.9	-26.2	-0.7	1
3798	1918-01-08	ROCKY MTN HOUSE	ALTA	3015523	-114.92	52.43	988	-14.6	-12.9	-1.7	1
3799	1918-01-12	ROCKY MTN HOUSE	ALTA	3015523	-114.92	52.43	988	-19.2	-19.1	-0.1	1
3800	1918-01-24	ROCKY MTN HOUSE	ALTA	3015523	-114.92	52.43	988	-8.5	-7.7	-0.8	1
3801	1918-01-25	ROCKY MTN HOUSE	ALTA	3015523	-114.92	52.43	988	-18.7	-18.6	-0.1	1
3802	1918-01-26	ROCKY MTN HOUSE	ALTA	3015523	-114.92	52.43	988	-18.2	-17	-1.2	1
3803	1918-02-13	ROCKY MTN HOUSE	ALTA	3015523	-114.92	52.43	988	-11	-4.3	-6.7	1
3804	1918-03-04	ROCKY MTN HOUSE	ALTA	3015523	-114.92	52.43	988	-26.9	-25.2	-1.7	1
3805	1918-04-01	ROCKY MTN HOUSE	ALTA	3015523	-114.92	52.43	988	-7.3	-6.3	-1	1
3806	1918-04-15	ROCKY MTN HOUSE	ALTA	3015523	-114.92	52.43	988	0.5	0.7	-0.2	1
3807	1918-05-25	ROCKY MTN HOUSE	ALTA	3015523	-114.92	52.43	988	-8.5	-5	-3.5	1

3808	1918-06-24	ROCKY MTN HOUSE	ALTA	3015523	-114.92	52.43	988	16.8	16.9	-0.1	1
3809	1918-07-14	ROCKY MTN HOUSE	ALTA	3015523	-114.92	52.43	988	15.6	16.4	-0.8	1
3810	1918-09-08	ROCKY MTN HOUSE	ALTA	3015523	-114.92	52.43	988	9.2	12.1	-2.9	1
3811	1918-11-04	ROCKY MTN HOUSE	ALTA	3015523	-114.92	52.43	988	-6.6	-5.7	-0.9	1
3812	1918-11-20	ROCKY MTN HOUSE	ALTA	3015523	-114.92	52.43	988	-5.2	-4.4	-0.8	1
3813	1918-12-11	ROCKY MTN HOUSE	ALTA	3015523	-114.92	52.43	988	-11	-10.5	-0.5	1
3814	1919-01-17	ROCKY MTN HOUSE	ALTA	3015523	-114.92	52.43	988	-12.3	-12	-0.3	1
3815	1919-02-27	ROCKY MTN HOUSE	ALTA	3015523	-114.92	52.43	988	-24.7	-24.2	-0.5	1
3816	1919-03-30	ROCKY MTN HOUSE	ALTA	3015523	-114.92	52.43	988	2.7	7.7	-5	1
3817	1919-04-12	ROCKY MTN HOUSE	ALTA	3015523	-114.92	52.43	988	1.7	6.7	-5	1
3818	1919-07-28	ROCKY MTN HOUSE	ALTA	3015523	-114.92	52.43	988	5.7	10.3	-4.6	1
3819	1919-08-31	ROCKY MTN HOUSE	ALTA	3015523	-114.92	52.43	988	8.5	9.6	-1.1	1
3820	1919-11-03	ROCKY MTN HOUSE	ALTA	3015523	-114.92	52.43	988	-11.1	-9.2	-1.9	1
3821	1919-11-23	ROCKY MTN HOUSE	ALTA	3015523	-114.92	52.43	988	-1.3	-1	-0.3	1
3822	1920-01-16	ROCKY MTN HOUSE	ALTA	3015523	-114.92	52.43	988	-11.1	-8.5	-2.6	1
3823	1920-01-17	ROCKY MTN HOUSE	ALTA	3015523	-114.92	52.43	988	-18.7	-18	-0.7	1
3824	1920-03-22	ROCKY MTN HOUSE	ALTA	3015523	-114.92	52.43	988	-0.7	-0.2	-0.5	1
3825	1920-04-05	ROCKY MTN HOUSE	ALTA	3015523	-114.92	52.43	988	-6.7	-2.5	-4.2	1
3826	1920-04-10	ROCKY MTN HOUSE	ALTA	3015523	-114.92	52.43	988	-3.9	-0.6	-3.3	1
3827	1921-07-02	ROCKY MTN HOUSE	ALTA	3015523	-114.92	52.43	988	7.8	13.6	-5.8	1
3828	1921-07-04	ROCKY MTN HOUSE	ALTA	3015523	-114.92	52.43	988	11	12.6	-1.6	1
3829	1921-08-17	ROCKY MTN HOUSE	ALTA	3015523	-114.92	52.43	988	11.6	12	-0.4	1
3830	1921-08-19	ROCKY MTN HOUSE	ALTA	3015523	-114.92	52.43	988	13.3	13.6	-0.3	1
3831	1921-09-25	ROCKY MTN HOUSE	ALTA	3015523	-114.92	52.43	988	15.5	17.5	-2	1
3832	1921-10-30	ROCKY MTN HOUSE	ALTA	3015523	-114.92	52.43	988	1.5	2.3	-0.8	1
3833	1921-11-18	ROCKY MTN HOUSE	ALTA	3015523	-114.92	52.43	988	-26.3	-24.1	-2.2	1
3834	1921-11-24	ROCKY MTN HOUSE	ALTA	3015523	-114.92	52.43	988	-25.8	-24.6	-1.2	1
3835	1921-11-26	ROCKY MTN HOUSE	ALTA	3015523	-114.92	52.43	988	-11.9	-9.2	-2.7	1
3836	1922-01-29	ROCKY MTN HOUSE	ALTA	3015523	-114.92	52.43	988	-22.4	-21	-1.4	1
3837	1922-02-08	ROCKY MTN HOUSE	ALTA	3015523	-114.92	52.43	988	-24.7	-24.6	-0.1	1
3838	1922-02-09	ROCKY MTN HOUSE	ALTA	3015523	-114.92	52.43	988	-28.5	-25.6	-2.9	1
3839	1922-04-04	ROCKY MTN HOUSE	ALTA	3015523	-114.92	52.43	988	-1.3	1.3	-2.6	1
3840	1922-05-10	ROCKY MTN HOUSE	ALTA	3015523	-114.92	52.43	988	6.4	7.6	-1.2	1
3841	1922-06-28	ROCKY MTN HOUSE	ALTA	3015523	-114.92	52.43	988	8.5	12.1	-3.6	1

3842	1922-08-05	ROCKY MTN HOUSE	ALTA	3015523	-114.92	52.43	988	16.2	16.4	-0.2	1
3843	1922-09-13	ROCKY MTN HOUSE	ALTA	3015523	-114.92	52.43	988	11	14.1	-3.1	1
3844	1922-09-15	ROCKY MTN HOUSE	ALTA	3015523	-114.92	52.43	988	13.3	14.7	-1.4	1
3845	1922-10-04	ROCKY MTN HOUSE	ALTA	3015523	-114.92	52.43	988	1	2.4	-1.4	1
3846	1922-10-31	ROCKY MTN HOUSE	ALTA	3015523	-114.92	52.43	988	-1.8	-0.6	-1.2	1
3847	1922-11-02	ROCKY MTN HOUSE	ALTA	3015523	-114.92	52.43	988	-5.3	-4.4	-0.9	1
3848	1923-01-01	ROCKY MTN HOUSE	ALTA	3015523	-114.92	52.43	988	-11.4	-10.5	-0.9	1
3849	1923-01-04	ROCKY MTN HOUSE	ALTA	3015523	-114.92	52.43	988	-15.2	-13.9	-1.3	1
3850	1923-05-28	ROCKY MTN HOUSE	ALTA	3015523	-114.92	52.43	988	1.5	2.4	-0.9	1
3851	1923-06-02	ROCKY MTN HOUSE	ALTA	3015523	-114.92	52.43	988	8.6	10.3	-1.7	1
3852	1923-06-04	ROCKY MTN HOUSE	ALTA	3015523	-114.92	52.43	988	10.4	12	-1.6	1
3853	1923-06-14	ROCKY MTN HOUSE	ALTA	3015523	-114.92	52.43	988	11.6	14.7	-3.1	1
3854	1923-06-22	ROCKY MTN HOUSE	ALTA	3015523	-114.92	52.43	988	8.6	14.1	-5.5	1
3855	1923-06-23	ROCKY MTN HOUSE	ALTA	3015523	-114.92	52.43	988	5	11	-6	1
3856	1923-06-24	ROCKY MTN HOUSE	ALTA	3015523	-114.92	52.43	988	12.4	12.6	-0.2	1
3857	1923-07-08	ROCKY MTN HOUSE	ALTA	3015523	-114.92	52.43	988	13.2	14.1	-0.9	1
3858	1923-07-09	ROCKY MTN HOUSE	ALTA	3015523	-114.92	52.43	988	12	14.7	-2.7	1
3859	1923-07-17	ROCKY MTN HOUSE	ALTA	3015523	-114.92	52.43	988	13.7	14.7	-1	1
3860	1923-07-31	ROCKY MTN HOUSE	ALTA	3015523	-114.92	52.43	988	4.3	6.8	-2.5	1
3861	1923-08-12	ROCKY MTN HOUSE	ALTA	3015523	-114.92	52.43	988	13.2	13.6	-0.4	1
3862	1923-08-19	ROCKY MTN HOUSE	ALTA	3015523	-114.92	52.43	988	12.4	14.1	-1.7	1
3863	1923-09-19	ROCKY MTN HOUSE	ALTA	3015523	-114.92	52.43	988	4.9	6.1	-1.2	1
3864	1923-09-20	ROCKY MTN HOUSE	ALTA	3015523	-114.92	52.43	988	1.4	2.4	-1	1
3865	1924-01-17	ROCKY MTN HOUSE	ALTA	3015523	-114.92	52.43	988	-22.4	-21.6	-0.8	1
3866	1924-01-25	ROCKY MTN HOUSE	ALTA	3015523	-114.92	52.43	988	-26.3	-26.2	-0.1	1
3867	1924-02-15	ROCKY MTN HOUSE	ALTA	3015523	-114.92	52.43	988	-20.8	-18.6	-2.2	1
3868	1924-03-13	ROCKY MTN HOUSE	ALTA	3015523	-114.92	52.43	988	-7.3	-5	-2.3	1
3869	1924-03-15	ROCKY MTN HOUSE	ALTA	3015523	-114.92	52.43	988	-1.3	-0.7	-0.6	1
3870	1924-03-19	ROCKY MTN HOUSE	ALTA	3015523	-114.92	52.43	988	-3.1	-2.5	-0.6	1
3871	1924-03-27	ROCKY MTN HOUSE	ALTA	3015523	-114.92	52.43	988	-7.3	-5.7	-1.6	1
3872	1924-04-11	ROCKY MTN HOUSE	ALTA	3015523	-114.92	52.43	988	-3	-2.5	-0.5	1
3873	1924-05-23	ROCKY MTN HOUSE	ALTA	3015523	-114.92	52.43	988	5.6	7.8	-2.2	1
3874	1924-06-14	ROCKY MTN HOUSE	ALTA	3015523	-114.92	52.43	988	6.3	12	-5.7	1
3875	1924-06-21	ROCKY MTN HOUSE	ALTA	3015523	-114.92	52.43	988	2.2	2.3	-0.1	1

3876	1924-07-29	ROCKY MTN HOUSE	ALTA	3015523	-114.92	52.43	988	13.7	14.1	-0.4	1
3877	1924-07-30	ROCKY MTN HOUSE	ALTA	3015523	-114.92	52.43	988	11	14.7	-3.7	1
3878	1924-07-31	ROCKY MTN HOUSE	ALTA	3015523	-114.92	52.43	988	13.2	13.6	-0.4	1
3879	1924-08-03	ROCKY MTN HOUSE	ALTA	3015523	-114.92	52.43	988	9.9	11.6	-1.7	1
3880	1924-08-04	ROCKY MTN HOUSE	ALTA	3015523	-114.92	52.43	988	5.7	7.8	-2.1	1
3881	1924-08-08	ROCKY MTN HOUSE	ALTA	3015523	-114.92	52.43	988	10.4	13.6	-3.2	1
3882	1924-08-30	ROCKY MTN HOUSE	ALTA	3015523	-114.92	52.43	988	2.2	3.4	-1.2	1
3883	1924-09-25	ROCKY MTN HOUSE	ALTA	3015523	-114.92	52.43	988	-0.3	0.6	-0.9	1
3884	1924-10-04	ROCKY MTN HOUSE	ALTA	3015523	-114.92	52.43	988	0.2	2.4	-2.2	1
3885	1924-11-02	ROCKY MTN HOUSE	ALTA	3015523	-114.92	52.43	988	-9	-6.4	-2.6	1
3886	1924-11-08	ROCKY MTN HOUSE	ALTA	3015523	-114.92	52.43	988	-14.7	-13.8	-0.9	1
3887	1924-12-07	ROCKY MTN HOUSE	ALTA	3015523	-114.92	52.43	988	-17.6	-15.3	-2.3	1
3888	1925-01-26	ROCKY MTN HOUSE	ALTA	3015523	-114.92	52.43	988	-7.3	-7.1	-0.2	1
3889	1925-01-27	ROCKY MTN HOUSE	ALTA	3015523	-114.92	52.43	988	-10.1	-5.8	-4.3	1
3890	1925-01-28	ROCKY MTN HOUSE	ALTA	3015523	-114.92	52.43	988	-7.4	-3.6	-3.8	1
3891	1925-03-18	ROCKY MTN HOUSE	ALTA	3015523	-114.92	52.43	988	-2.4	1.4	-3.8	1
3892	1925-04-02	ROCKY MTN HOUSE	ALTA	3015523	-114.92	52.43	988	-6	-0.6	-5.4	1
3893	1925-04-04	ROCKY MTN HOUSE	ALTA	3015523	-114.92	52.43	988	0.2	2.3	-2.1	1
3894	1925-04-05	ROCKY MTN HOUSE	ALTA	3015523	-114.92	52.43	988	1.5	4	-2.5	1
3895	1925-04-06	ROCKY MTN HOUSE	ALTA	3015523	-114.92	52.43	988	3	12	-9	1
3896	1925-04-23	ROCKY MTN HOUSE	ALTA	3015523	-114.92	52.43	988	5	5.3	-0.3	1
3897	1925-04-25	ROCKY MTN HOUSE	ALTA	3015523	-114.92	52.43	988	2.3	3.4	-1.1	1
3898	1925-05-22	ROCKY MTN HOUSE	ALTA	3015523	-114.92	52.43	988	13.7	14.7	-1	1
3899	1925-06-04	ROCKY MTN HOUSE	ALTA	3015523	-114.92	52.43	988	2.3	6	-3.7	1
3900	1925-06-05	ROCKY MTN HOUSE	ALTA	3015523	-114.92	52.43	988	3.8	9.5	-5.7	1
3901	1925-06-13	ROCKY MTN HOUSE	ALTA	3015523	-114.92	52.43	988	11.9	12	-0.1	1
3902	1925-07-07	ROCKY MTN HOUSE	ALTA	3015523	-114.92	52.43	988	10.4	11	-0.6	1
3903	1925-07-23	ROCKY MTN HOUSE	ALTA	3015523	-114.92	52.43	988	11.9	12.1	-0.2	1
3904	1925-08-15	ROCKY MTN HOUSE	ALTA	3015523	-114.92	52.43	988	9.2	13.6	-4.4	1
3905	1925-08-16	ROCKY MTN HOUSE	ALTA	3015523	-114.92	52.43	988	7.8	13.6	-5.8	1
3906	1925-08-17	ROCKY MTN HOUSE	ALTA	3015523	-114.92	52.43	988	5	13.6	-8.6	1
3907	1925-08-18	ROCKY MTN HOUSE	ALTA	3015523	-114.92	52.43	988	9.9	12.1	-2.2	1
3908	1925-08-22	ROCKY MTN HOUSE	ALTA	3015523	-114.92	52.43	988	4.3	6.1	-1.8	1
3909	1925-08-23	ROCKY MTN HOUSE	ALTA	3015523	-114.92	52.43	988	1.1	4.8	-3.7	1

3910	1925-08-24	ROCKY MTN HOUSE	ALTA	3015523	-114.92	52.43	988	5.8	6	-0.2	1
3911	1925-09-05	ROCKY MTN HOUSE	ALTA	3015523	-114.92	52.43	988	5	11	-6	1
3912	1925-09-06	ROCKY MTN HOUSE	ALTA	3015523	-114.92	52.43	988	3	9.5	-6.5	1
3913	1925-09-10	ROCKY MTN HOUSE	ALTA	3015523	-114.92	52.43	988	4.3	5.4	-1.1	1
3914	1925-09-11	ROCKY MTN HOUSE	ALTA	3015523	-114.92	52.43	988	7.1	8.8	-1.7	1
3915	1925-09-12	ROCKY MTN HOUSE	ALTA	3015523	-114.92	52.43	988	5.7	11	-5.3	1
3916	1925-09-17	ROCKY MTN HOUSE	ALTA	3015523	-114.92	52.43	988	0.5	2.7	-2.2	1
3917	1925-09-19	ROCKY MTN HOUSE	ALTA	3015523	-114.92	52.43	988	-0.7	1.4	-2.1	1
3918	1925-09-27	ROCKY MTN HOUSE	ALTA	3015523	-114.92	52.43	988	-0.8	-0.2	-0.6	1
3919	1925-09-29	ROCKY MTN HOUSE	ALTA	3015523	-114.92	52.43	988	-1.3	2.6	-3.9	1
3920	1925-10-06	ROCKY MTN HOUSE	ALTA	3015523	-114.92	52.43	988	-6	-2.5	-3.5	1
3921	1925-10-07	ROCKY MTN HOUSE	ALTA	3015523	-114.92	52.43	988	-6	-3.1	-2.9	1
3922	1925-10-19	ROCKY MTN HOUSE	ALTA	3015523	-114.92	52.43	988	-1.8	-0.2	-1.6	1
3923	1925-11-06	ROCKY MTN HOUSE	ALTA	3015523	-114.92	52.43	988	-13.3	-12.8	-0.5	1
3924	1925-11-24	ROCKY MTN HOUSE	ALTA	3015523	-114.92	52.43	988	-1.8	-0.2	-1.6	1
3925	1925-11-27	ROCKY MTN HOUSE	ALTA	3015523	-114.92	52.43	988	-13.8	-12	-1.8	1
3926	1925-11-28	ROCKY MTN HOUSE	ALTA	3015523	-114.92	52.43	988	-2.4	-0.2	-2.2	1
3927	1925-11-29	ROCKY MTN HOUSE	ALTA	3015523	-114.92	52.43	988	-1.3	-0.2	-1.1	1
3928	1925-11-30	ROCKY MTN HOUSE	ALTA	3015523	-114.92	52.43	988	-2.5	1.3	-3.8	1
3929	1925-12-14	ROCKY MTN HOUSE	ALTA	3015523	-114.92	52.43	988	-5.4	-4.4	-1	1
3930	1925-12-20	ROCKY MTN HOUSE	ALTA	3015523	-114.92	52.43	988	-11.9	-9.2	-2.7	1
3931	1925-12-21	ROCKY MTN HOUSE	ALTA	3015523	-114.92	52.43	988	-10.9	-6.4	-4.5	1
3932	1925-12-22	ROCKY MTN HOUSE	ALTA	3015523	-114.92	52.43	988	-10.5	-7.8	-2.7	1
3933	1925-12-24	ROCKY MTN HOUSE	ALTA	3015523	-114.92	52.43	988	-12.9	-11.1	-1.8	1
3934	1926-01-26	ROCKY MTN HOUSE	ALTA	3015523	-114.92	52.43	988	-1.3	-0.6	-0.7	1
3935	1926-02-13	ROCKY MTN HOUSE	ALTA	3015523	-114.92	52.43	988	-10.1	-9.9	-0.2	1
3936	1926-03-05	ROCKY MTN HOUSE	ALTA	3015523	-114.92	52.43	988	-0.3	-0.2	-0.1	1
3937	1926-03-26	ROCKY MTN HOUSE	ALTA	3015523	-114.92	52.43	988	-1.8	-1.6	-0.2	1
3938	1926-08-08	ROCKY MTN HOUSE	ALTA	3015523	-114.92	52.43	988	9.2	11.6	-2.4	1
3939	1926-08-14	ROCKY MTN HOUSE	ALTA	3015523	-114.92	52.43	988	5.6	12.6	-7	1
3940	1926-08-27	ROCKY MTN HOUSE	ALTA	3015523	-114.92	52.43	988	14.3	14.7	-0.4	1
3941	1926-08-31	ROCKY MTN HOUSE	ALTA	3015523	-114.92	52.43	988	14.8	17.5	-2.7	1
3942	1926-09-02	ROCKY MTN HOUSE	ALTA	3015523	-114.92	52.43	988	5.6	14.1	-8.5	1
3943	1926-09-03	ROCKY MTN HOUSE	ALTA	3015523	-114.92	52.43	988	6.3	14.7	-8.4	1

3944	1926-09-16	ROCKY MTN HOUSE	ALTA	3015523	-114.92	52.43	988	-4.6	-1.5	-3.1	1
3945	1926-09-17	ROCKY MTN HOUSE	ALTA	3015523	-114.92	52.43	988	-3.9	-3.1	-0.8	1
3946	1926-09-22	ROCKY MTN HOUSE	ALTA	3015523	-114.92	52.43	988	-6.1	-4.3	-1.8	1
3947	1926-10-11	ROCKY MTN HOUSE	ALTA	3015523	-114.92	52.43	988	-4.7	-3.6	-1.1	1
3948	1926-10-13	ROCKY MTN HOUSE	ALTA	3015523	-114.92	52.43	988	-3.7	-3.6	-0.1	1
3949	1926-10-16	ROCKY MTN HOUSE	ALTA	3015523	-114.92	52.43	988	-3.1	-2.5	-0.6	1
3950	1926-11-09	ROCKY MTN HOUSE	ALTA	3015523	-114.92	52.43	988	-6.1	-5	-1.1	1
3951	1926-11-10	ROCKY MTN HOUSE	ALTA	3015523	-114.92	52.43	988	-4.6	-3.7	-0.9	1
3952	1926-11-12	ROCKY MTN HOUSE	ALTA	3015523	-114.92	52.43	988	-0.8	-0.2	-0.6	1
3953	1926-11-13	ROCKY MTN HOUSE	ALTA	3015523	-114.92	52.43	988	-1.8	-1	-0.8	1
3954	1926-11-22	ROCKY MTN HOUSE	ALTA	3015523	-114.92	52.43	988	-12.8	-9.2	-3.6	1
3955	1926-11-26	ROCKY MTN HOUSE	ALTA	3015523	-114.92	52.43	988	-16.6	-14.3	-2.3	1
3956	1926-11-27	ROCKY MTN HOUSE	ALTA	3015523	-114.92	52.43	988	-15.6	-15.3	-0.3	1
3957	1926-11-29	ROCKY MTN HOUSE	ALTA	3015523	-114.92	52.43	988	-15.6	-15.3	-0.3	1
3958	1926-11-30	ROCKY MTN HOUSE	ALTA	3015523	-114.92	52.43	988	-18.7	-18.6	-0.1	1
3959	1927-01-17	ROCKY MTN HOUSE	ALTA	3015523	-114.92	52.43	988	-20.8	-20.1	-0.7	1
3960	1927-03-01	ROCKY MTN HOUSE	ALTA	3015523	-114.92	52.43	988	-12.3	-11.6	-0.7	1
3961	1927-04-01	ROCKY MTN HOUSE	ALTA	3015523	-114.92	52.43	988	-11	-7.8	-3.2	1
3962	1927-04-20	ROCKY MTN HOUSE	ALTA	3015523	-114.92	52.43	988	-8.5	-4.3	-4.2	1
3963	1927-05-02	ROCKY MTN HOUSE	ALTA	3015523	-114.92	52.43	988	-0.3	1.4	-1.7	1
3964	1927-05-03	ROCKY MTN HOUSE	ALTA	3015523	-114.92	52.43	988	2.6	4.1	-1.5	1
3965	1927-05-18	ROCKY MTN HOUSE	ALTA	3015523	-114.92	52.43	988	3.8	4.8	-1	1
3966	1927-05-20	ROCKY MTN HOUSE	ALTA	3015523	-114.92	52.43	988	3.3	7.6	-4.3	1
3967	1927-05-29	ROCKY MTN HOUSE	ALTA	3015523	-114.92	52.43	988	6.4	8.4	-2	1
3968	1927-05-30	ROCKY MTN HOUSE	ALTA	3015523	-114.92	52.43	988	6.4	7.6	-1.2	1
3969	1927-06-10	ROCKY MTN HOUSE	ALTA	3015523	-114.92	52.43	988	7.8	12.1	-4.3	1
3970	1927-06-20	ROCKY MTN HOUSE	ALTA	3015523	-114.92	52.43	988	9.2	12.6	-3.4	1
3971	1927-08-19	ROCKY MTN HOUSE	ALTA	3015523	-114.92	52.43	988	12.5	13.1	-0.6	1
3972	1927-09-07	ROCKY MTN HOUSE	ALTA	3015523	-114.92	52.43	988	4.9	7.5	-2.6	1
3973	1927-09-29	ROCKY MTN HOUSE	ALTA	3015523	-114.92	52.43	988	5.7	7.8	-2.1	1
3974	1927-09-30	ROCKY MTN HOUSE	ALTA	3015523	-114.92	52.43	988	4.9	8.8	-3.9	1
3975	1927-11-07	ROCKY MTN HOUSE	ALTA	3015523	-114.92	52.43	988	-7.9	-7.7	-0.2	1
3976	1927-12-01	ROCKY MTN HOUSE	ALTA	3015523	-114.92	52.43	988	-19.8	-18.6	-1.2	1
3977	1927-12-16	ROCKY MTN HOUSE	ALTA	3015523	-114.92	52.43	988	-6.1	-2.5	-3.6	1

3978	1927-12-29	ROCKY MTN HOUSE	ALTA	3015523	-114.92	52.43	988	-27.4	-26.2	-1.2	1
3979	1928-01-10	ROCKY MTN HOUSE	ALTA	3015523	-114.92	52.43	988	-8.5	-4.3	-4.2	1
3980	1928-03-28	ROCKY MTN HOUSE	ALTA	3015523	-114.92	52.43	988	-2.5	-1.9	-0.6	1
3981	1928-06-08	ROCKY MTN HOUSE	ALTA	3015523	-114.92	52.43	988	8.6	8.8	-0.2	1
3982	1928-06-19	ROCKY MTN HOUSE	ALTA	3015523	-114.92	52.43	988	1.7	10.3	-8.6	1
3983	1928-06-20	ROCKY MTN HOUSE	ALTA	3015523	-114.92	52.43	988	8.5	9.6	-1.1	1
3984	1928-07-01	ROCKY MTN HOUSE	ALTA	3015523	-114.92	52.43	988	7.2	11.6	-4.4	1
3985	1928-10-28	ROCKY MTN HOUSE	ALTA	3015523	-114.92	52.43	988	-3.9	-3.1	-0.8	1
3986	1929-01-06	ROCKY MTN HOUSE	ALTA	3015523	-114.92	52.43	988	-3.9	-1.7	-2.2	1
3987	1929-01-19	ROCKY MTN HOUSE	ALTA	3015523	-114.92	52.43	988	-13.7	-12.1	-1.6	1
3988	1929-05-04	ROCKY MTN HOUSE	ALTA	3015523	-114.92	52.43	988	-2.4	-0.5	-1.9	1
3989	1929-06-02	ROCKY MTN HOUSE	ALTA	3015523	-114.92	52.43	988	6.4	10.9	-4.5	1
3990	1929-06-03	ROCKY MTN HOUSE	ALTA	3015523	-114.92	52.43	988	4.9	10.3	-5.4	1
3991	1929-09-23	ROCKY MTN HOUSE	ALTA	3015523	-114.92	52.43	988	0.2	0.5	-0.3	1
3992	1929-09-24	ROCKY MTN HOUSE	ALTA	3015523	-114.92	52.43	988	0.6	1.6	-1	1
3993	1929-11-16	ROCKY MTN HOUSE	ALTA	3015523	-114.92	52.43	988	1	1.4	-0.4	1
3994	1929-12-10	ROCKY MTN HOUSE	ALTA	3015523	-114.92	52.43	988	-23	-21.6	-1.4	1
3995	1929-12-15	ROCKY MTN HOUSE	ALTA	3015523	-114.92	52.43	988	-23.6	-20.1	-3.5	1
3996	1929-12-17	ROCKY MTN HOUSE	ALTA	3015523	-114.92	52.43	988	-18.1	-17	-1.1	1
3997	1930-01-10	ROCKY MTN HOUSE	ALTA	3015523	-114.92	52.43	988	-25.2	-21.1	-4.1	1
3998	1930-02-09	ROCKY MTN HOUSE	ALTA	3015523	-114.92	52.43	988	-5.3	-4.4	-0.9	1
3999	1930-02-26	ROCKY MTN HOUSE	ALTA	3015523	-114.92	52.43	988	-3.8	-3.1	-0.7	1
4000	1930-03-05	ROCKY MTN HOUSE	ALTA	3015523	-114.92	52.43	988	-3.8	-1.6	-2.2	1
4001	1930-03-07	ROCKY MTN HOUSE	ALTA	3015523	-114.92	52.43	988	0.6	3.4	-2.8	1
4002	1930-03-10	ROCKY MTN HOUSE	ALTA	3015523	-114.92	52.43	988	0.5	4.8	-4.3	1
4003	1930-03-14	ROCKY MTN HOUSE	ALTA	3015523	-114.92	52.43	988	-9.6	-7.8	-1.8	1
4004	1930-03-15	ROCKY MTN HOUSE	ALTA	3015523	-114.92	52.43	988	-8.5	-7.8	-0.7	1
4005	1930-03-17	ROCKY MTN HOUSE	ALTA	3015523	-114.92	52.43	988	0.2	4.1	-3.9	1
4006	1930-03-18	ROCKY MTN HOUSE	ALTA	3015523	-114.92	52.43	988	7.1	8.6	-1.5	1
4007	1930-03-26	ROCKY MTN HOUSE	ALTA	3015523	-114.92	52.43	988	-1.8	0.4	-2.2	1
4008	1930-03-27	ROCKY MTN HOUSE	ALTA	3015523	-114.92	52.43	988	2.6	8.6	-6	1
4009	1930-05-30	ROCKY MTN HOUSE	ALTA	3015523	-114.92	52.43	988	4.3	8.8	-4.5	1
4010	1930-06-14	ROCKY MTN HOUSE	ALTA	3015523	-114.92	52.43	988	7.1	8.8	-1.7	1
4011	1930-06-21	ROCKY MTN HOUSE	ALTA	3015523	-114.92	52.43	988	5	6	-1	1

4012	1930-06-27	ROCKY MTN HOUSE	ALTA	3015523	-114.92	52.43	988	9.2	11.6	-2.4	1
4013	1930-08-20	ROCKY MTN HOUSE	ALTA	3015523	-114.92	52.43	988	11.5	11.6	-0.1	1
4014	1930-09-07	ROCKY MTN HOUSE	ALTA	3015523	-114.92	52.43	988	11	12	-1	1
4015	1930-09-08	ROCKY MTN HOUSE	ALTA	3015523	-114.92	52.43	988	7.1	11.6	-4.5	1
4016	1930-09-11	ROCKY MTN HOUSE	ALTA	3015523	-114.92	52.43	988	10.4	11.6	-1.2	1
4017	1930-09-29	ROCKY MTN HOUSE	ALTA	3015523	-114.92	52.43	988	2.9	4.1	-1.2	1
4018	1930-10-11	ROCKY MTN HOUSE	ALTA	3015523	-114.92	52.43	988	-5.3	-5.1	-0.2	1
4019	1930-10-18	ROCKY MTN HOUSE	ALTA	3015523	-114.92	52.43	988	-12.3	-11.6	-0.7	1
4020	1930-10-27	ROCKY MTN HOUSE	ALTA	3015523	-114.92	52.43	988	2.9	4.1	-1.2	1
4021	1930-11-13	ROCKY MTN HOUSE	ALTA	3015523	-114.92	52.43	988	-15.6	-13.3	-2.3	1
4022	1930-11-14	ROCKY MTN HOUSE	ALTA	3015523	-114.92	52.43	988	-16.1	-13.3	-2.8	1
4023	1930-11-18	ROCKY MTN HOUSE	ALTA	3015523	-114.92	52.43	988	-9	-5	-4	1
4024	1930-11-19	ROCKY MTN HOUSE	ALTA	3015523	-114.92	52.43	988	-6.6	-4.3	-2.3	1
4025	1930-11-20	ROCKY MTN HOUSE	ALTA	3015523	-114.92	52.43	988	0.2	4.1	-3.9	1
4026	1930-11-22	ROCKY MTN HOUSE	ALTA	3015523	-114.92	52.43	988	0.6	2.4	-1.8	1
4027	1930-11-23	ROCKY MTN HOUSE	ALTA	3015523	-114.92	52.43	988	2.9	4.8	-1.9	1
4028	1930-11-27	ROCKY MTN HOUSE	ALTA	3015523	-114.92	52.43	988	-1.8	-1.7	-0.1	1
4029	1930-12-06	ROCKY MTN HOUSE	ALTA	3015523	-114.92	52.43	988	1.5	2.4	-0.9	1
4030	1930-12-07	ROCKY MTN HOUSE	ALTA	3015523	-114.92	52.43	988	11.6	13.6	-2	1
4031	1930-12-08	ROCKY MTN HOUSE	ALTA	3015523	-114.92	52.43	988	5.7	12	-6.3	1
4032	1930-12-12	ROCKY MTN HOUSE	ALTA	3015523	-114.92	52.43	988	0.6	1.4	-0.8	1
4033	1930-12-14	ROCKY MTN HOUSE	ALTA	3015523	-114.92	52.43	988	1.4	3.3	-1.9	1
4034	1930-12-19	ROCKY MTN HOUSE	ALTA	3015523	-114.92	52.43	988	6.4	6.9	-0.5	1
4035	1931-01-07	ROCKY MTN HOUSE	ALTA	3015523	-114.92	52.43	988	-7.9	-6.3	-1.6	1
4036	1931-02-02	ROCKY MTN HOUSE	ALTA	3015523	-114.92	52.43	988	-11	-9.2	-1.8	1
4037	1931-04-22	ROCKY MTN HOUSE	ALTA	3015523	-114.92	52.43	988	11.5	12.6	-1.1	1
4038	1931-04-24	ROCKY MTN HOUSE	ALTA	3015523	-114.92	52.43	988	15.6	15.8	-0.2	1
4039	1931-04-28	ROCKY MTN HOUSE	ALTA	3015523	-114.92	52.43	988	16.9	19	-2.1	1
4040	1931-04-30	ROCKY MTN HOUSE	ALTA	3015523	-114.92	52.43	988	12.5	14.7	-2.2	1
4041	1931-05-15	ROCKY MTN HOUSE	ALTA	3015523	-114.92	52.43	988	12.4	13.6	-1.2	1
4042	1931-05-22	ROCKY MTN HOUSE	ALTA	3015523	-114.92	52.43	988	14.9	17.5	-2.6	1
4043	1931-05-26	ROCKY MTN HOUSE	ALTA	3015523	-114.92	52.43	988	20.4	21.4	-1	1
4044	1931-05-28	ROCKY MTN HOUSE	ALTA	3015523	-114.92	52.43	988	18.5	19.6	-1.1	1
4045	1931-05-29	ROCKY MTN HOUSE	ALTA	3015523	-114.92	52.43	988	17.4	18	-0.6	1

4046	1931-05-31	ROCKY MTN HOUSE	ALTA	3015523	-114.92	52.43	988	19.2	19.6	-0.4	1
4047	1931-06-10	ROCKY MTN HOUSE	ALTA	3015523	-114.92	52.43	988	20.4	21.4	-1	1
4048	1931-06-15	ROCKY MTN HOUSE	ALTA	3015523	-114.92	52.43	988	15.9	16.9	-1	1
4049	1931-06-22	ROCKY MTN HOUSE	ALTA	3015523	-114.92	52.43	988	20.4	21.4	-1	1
4050	1931-06-23	ROCKY MTN HOUSE	ALTA	3015523	-114.92	52.43	988	18	19	-1	1
4051	1931-06-26	ROCKY MTN HOUSE	ALTA	3015523	-114.92	52.43	988	17.4	19.6	-2.2	1
4052	1931-06-28	ROCKY MTN HOUSE	ALTA	3015523	-114.92	52.43	988	14.9	17.5	-2.6	1
4053	1931-06-29	ROCKY MTN HOUSE	ALTA	3015523	-114.92	52.43	988	9	12.6	-3.6	1
4054	1931-06-30	ROCKY MTN HOUSE	ALTA	3015523	-114.92	52.43	988	6.7	9.6	-2.9	1
4055	1931-07-01	ROCKY MTN HOUSE	ALTA	3015523	-114.92	52.43	988	15.3	17.5	-2.2	1
4056	1931-07-04	ROCKY MTN HOUSE	ALTA	3015523	-114.92	52.43	988	19.9	22.5	-2.6	1
4057	1931-07-14	ROCKY MTN HOUSE	ALTA	3015523	-114.92	52.43	988	12.8	16.4	-3.6	1
4058	1931-07-16	ROCKY MTN HOUSE	ALTA	3015523	-114.92	52.43	988	18.6	23.5	-4.9	1
4059	1931-11-26	ROCKY MTN HOUSE	ALTA	3015523	-114.92	52.43	988	-10	-9.9	-0.1	1
4060	1931-12-24	ROCKY MTN HOUSE	ALTA	3015523	-114.92	52.43	988	-10.3	-8.4	-1.9	1
4061	1931-12-28	ROCKY MTN HOUSE	ALTA	3015523	-114.92	52.43	988	-10.3	-8.4	-1.9	1
4062	1933-01-08	ROCKY MTN HOUSE	ALTA	3015523	-114.92	52.43	988	-9.9	-9.8	-0.1	1
4063	1933-03-07	ROCKY MTN HOUSE	ALTA	3015523	-114.92	52.43	988	-10.3	-9.1	-1.2	1
4064	1933-09-01	ROCKY MTN HOUSE	ALTA	3015523	-114.92	52.43	988	9.7	13.1	-3.4	1
4065	1933-10-23	ROCKY MTN HOUSE	ALTA	3015523	-114.92	52.43	988	-8.5	-6.3	-2.2	1
4066	1934-09-26	ROCKY MTN HOUSE	ALTA	3015523	-114.92	52.43	988	7.8	9.4	-1.6	1
4067	1934-11-21	ROCKY MTN HOUSE	ALTA	3015523	-114.92	52.43	988	-9.9	-9.2	-0.7	1
4068	1934-11-26	ROCKY MTN HOUSE	ALTA	3015523	-114.92	52.43	988	-10.3	-9.9	-0.4	1
4069	1934-12-25	ROCKY MTN HOUSE	ALTA	3015523	-114.92	52.43	988	-31.4	-30.4	-1	1
4070	1935-01-06	ROCKY MTN HOUSE	ALTA	3015523	-114.92	52.43	988	-10.3	-9.9	-0.4	1
4071	1935-02-23	ROCKY MTN HOUSE	ALTA	3015523	-114.92	52.43	988	-10.8	-9.8	-1	1
4072	1935-02-27	ROCKY MTN HOUSE	ALTA	3015523	-114.92	52.43	988	-11.4	-9.8	-1.6	1
4073	1935-04-05	ROCKY MTN HOUSE	ALTA	3015523	-114.92	52.43	988	-11.8	-11.6	-0.2	1
4074	1935-04-13	ROCKY MTN HOUSE	ALTA	3015523	-114.92	52.43	988	-10.8	-9.8	-1	1
4075	1935-11-01	ROCKY MTN HOUSE	ALTA	3015523	-114.92	52.43	988	-11.8	-9.8	-2	1
4076	1935-11-12	ROCKY MTN HOUSE	ALTA	3015523	-114.92	52.43	988	-10.8	-10.5	-0.3	1
4077	1996-11-14	ROCKY MTN HOUSE	ALTA	3015523	-114.92	52.43	988	-11.8	-11.3	-0.5	1
4078	1996-11-15	ROCKY MTN HOUSE	ALTA	3015523	-114.92	52.43	988	-16.1	-15.6	-0.5	1
4079	1998-12-17	ROCKY MTN HOUSE	ALTA	3015523	-114.92	52.43	988	-14	-5.2	-8.8	1

4080	1998-12-27	ROCKY MTN HOUSE	ALTA	3015523	-114.92	52.43	988	-17.6	-17.1	-0.5	1
4081	1992-04-18	WASKESIU LAKE	SASK	4068559	-106.07	53.92	569	3	5	-2	1
4082	1992-05-19	WASKESIU LAKE	SASK	4068559	-106.07	53.92	569	2.5	11.5	-9	1
4083	1939-11-02	PARRSBORO	NS	8204402	-64.33	45.4	31	8.3	8.5	-0.2	1
4084	2013-11-19	BARKERVILLE	BC	1090660	-121.52	53.07	1283	-17	-16	-1	1
4085	1914-11-02	AMOS	QUE	709CEE9	-78.13	48.57	305	-5.8	-5.7	-0.1	1
4086	1914-11-12	AMOS	QUE	709CEE9	-78.13	48.57	305	-10.5	-10.3	-0.2	1
4087	1914-11-22	AMOS	QUE	709CEE9	-78.13	48.57	305	-11.9	-11.1	-0.8	1
4088	1915-11-09	AMOS	QUE	709CEE9	-78.13	48.57	305	-0.7	0.1	-0.8	1
4089	1915-11-15	AMOS	QUE	709CEE9	-78.13	48.57	305	-5.2	-4.5	-0.7	1
4090	1915-12-10	AMOS	QUE	709CEE9	-78.13	48.57	305	-10.6	-10.3	-0.3	1
4091	1915-12-16	AMOS	QUE	709CEE9	-78.13	48.57	305	-7.6	-7.1	-0.5	1
4092	1915-12-18	AMOS	QUE	709CEE9	-78.13	48.57	305	-7.6	-7.1	-0.5	1
4093	1915-12-19	AMOS	QUE	709CEE9	-78.13	48.57	305	-7.6	-7.5	-0.1	1
4094	1915-12-24	AMOS	QUE	709CEE9	-78.13	48.57	305	-10.1	-9.4	-0.7	1
4095	1916-01-02	AMOS	QUE	709CEE9	-78.13	48.57	305	-9.7	-9	-0.7	1
4096	1916-01-25	AMOS	QUE	709CEE9	-78.13	48.57	305	-10.5	-10.3	-0.2	1
4097	1916-02-17	AMOS	QUE	709CEE9	-78.13	48.57	305	-7.6	-6.5	-1.1	1
4098	1916-02-25	AMOS	QUE	709CEE9	-78.13	48.57	305	-9.2	-6.5	-2.7	1
4099	1916-03-27	AMOS	QUE	709CEE9	-78.13	48.57	305	-4.1	-3	-1.1	1
4100	1916-10-09	AMOS	QUE	709CEE9	-78.13	48.57	305	3.5	4.7	-1.2	1
4101	1916-11-11	AMOS	QUE	709CEE9	-78.13	48.57	305	-10.6	-8.9	-1.7	1
4102	1916-11-24	AMOS	QUE	709CEE9	-78.13	48.57	305	-4.7	-3.5	-1.2	1
4103	1916-12-07	AMOS	QUE	709CEE9	-78.13	48.57	305	-3.6	-3	-0.6	1
4104	1916-12-10	AMOS	QUE	709CEE9	-78.13	48.57	305	-11.3	-8.9	-2.4	1
4105	1916-12-28	AMOS	QUE	709CEE9	-78.13	48.57	305	-10.6	-8.9	-1.7	1
4106	1917-01-08	AMOS	QUE	709CEE9	-78.13	48.57	305	-17.2	-16.6	-0.6	1
4107	1917-01-14	AMOS	QUE	709CEE9	-78.13	48.57	305	-12.2	-11.1	-1.1	1
4108	1917-01-18	AMOS	QUE	709CEE9	-78.13	48.57	305	-19.3	-17.5	-1.8	1
4109	1917-01-30	AMOS	QUE	709CEE9	-78.13	48.57	305	-11.2	-11.1	-0.1	1
4110	1917-03-18	AMOS	QUE	709CEE9	-78.13	48.57	305	-11.2	-8.9	-2.3	1
4111	1917-03-27	AMOS	QUE	709CEE9	-78.13	48.57	305	-1.8	-0.3	-1.5	1
4112	1917-04-07	AMOS	QUE	709CEE9	-78.13	48.57	305	-5.8	-5.7	-0.1	1
4113	1917-11-18	AMOS	QUE	709CEE9	-78.13	48.57	305	-5.8	-4.4	-1.4	1

4114	1917-11-22	AMOS	QUE	709CEE9	-78.13	48.57	305	-11	-9.4	-1.6	1
4115	1917-11-23	AMOS	QUE	709CEE9	-78.13	48.57	305	-11.5	-10.7	-0.8	1
4116	1917-11-24	AMOS	QUE	709CEE9	-78.13	48.57	305	-10.6	-9.9	-0.7	1
4117	1917-12-09	AMOS	QUE	709CEE9	-78.13	48.57	305	-18.2	-17.1	-1.1	1
4118	1917-12-25	AMOS	QUE	709CEE9	-78.13	48.57	305	-19.9	-18.4	-1.5	1
4119	1918-01-10	AMOS	QUE	709CEE9	-78.13	48.57	305	-17.7	-16.5	-1.2	1
4120	1918-02-14	AMOS	QUE	709CEE9	-78.13	48.57	305	-11.5	-9.4	-2.1	1
4121	1918-03-25	AMOS	QUE	709CEE9	-78.13	48.57	305	-6.4	-5.7	-0.7	1
4122	1918-04-08	AMOS	QUE	709CEE9	-78.13	48.57	305	-4.7	-3.5	-1.2	1
4123	1918-04-22	AMOS	QUE	709CEE9	-78.13	48.57	305	2.9	3.1	-0.2	1
4124	1918-04-30	AMOS	QUE	709CEE9	-78.13	48.57	305	0.6	0.9	-0.3	1
4125	1918-11-18	AMOS	QUE	709CEE9	-78.13	48.57	305	4.1	4.7	-0.6	1
4126	1918-11-25	AMOS	QUE	709CEE9	-78.13	48.57	305	-11.1	-9.5	-1.6	1
4127	1918-11-30	AMOS	QUE	709CEE9	-78.13	48.57	305	-10.1	-9.9	-0.2	1
4128	1918-12-15	AMOS	QUE	709CEE9	-78.13	48.57	305	-5.8	-4.4	-1.4	1
4129	1918-12-16	AMOS	QUE	709CEE9	-78.13	48.57	305	-9.7	-8.5	-1.2	1
4130	1918-12-23	AMOS	QUE	709CEE9	-78.13	48.57	305	-11.8	-10.3	-1.5	1
4131	1919-02-05	AMOS	QUE	709CEE9	-78.13	48.57	305	-7.6	-7.1	-0.5	1
4132	1919-03-04	AMOS	QUE	709CEE9	-78.13	48.57	305	-11.4	-9.8	-1.6	1
4133	1919-03-27	AMOS	QUE	709CEE9	-78.13	48.57	305	-11	-9.8	-1.2	1
4134	1919-04-24	AMOS	QUE	709CEE9	-78.13	48.57	305	-7	-5.3	-1.7	1
4135	1919-09-22	AMOS	QUE	709CEE9	-78.13	48.57	305	5.5	6.4	-0.9	1
4136	1919-11-01	AMOS	QUE	709CEE9	-78.13	48.57	305	-1.8	-0.9	-0.9	1
4137	1919-11-30	AMOS	QUE	709CEE9	-78.13	48.57	305	-9.7	-7.5	-2.2	1
4138	1919-12-05	AMOS	QUE	709CEE9	-78.13	48.57	305	-10.6	-8.9	-1.7	1
4139	1919-12-30	AMOS	QUE	709CEE9	-78.13	48.57	305	-18.2	-17.5	-0.7	1
4140	1920-01-08	AMOS	QUE	709CEE9	-78.13	48.57	305	-12.8	-12.4	-0.4	1
4141	1920-01-14	AMOS	QUE	709CEE9	-78.13	48.57	305	-19.3	-18.4	-0.9	1
4142	1920-01-30	AMOS	QUE	709CEE9	-78.13	48.57	305	-26	-25	-1	1
4143	1920-02-08	AMOS	QUE	709CEE9	-78.13	48.57	305	-8.7	-8.6	-0.1	1
4144	1920-02-11	AMOS	QUE	709CEE9	-78.13	48.57	305	-7.6	-7.5	-0.1	1
4145	1920-02-15	AMOS	QUE	709CEE9	-78.13	48.57	305	-12.8	-11.4	-1.4	1
4146	1920-02-20	AMOS	QUE	709CEE9	-78.13	48.57	305	-12.5	-12.4	-0.1	1
4147	1920-02-27	AMOS	QUE	709CEE9	-78.13	48.57	305	-28.8	-27	-1.8	1

4148	1920-03-12	AMOS	QUE	709CEE9	-78.13	48.57	305	-9.7	-7.5	-2.2	1
4149	1920-03-17	AMOS	QUE	709CEE9	-78.13	48.57	305	-8.1	-8	-0.1	1
4150	1920-11-09	AMOS	QUE	709CEE9	-78.13	48.57	305	-7	-5.3	-1.7	1
4151	1920-12-02	AMOS	QUE	709CEE9	-78.13	48.57	305	-6.4	-4.8	-1.6	1
4152	1920-12-07	AMOS	QUE	709CEE9	-78.13	48.57	305	-11.1	-8.9	-2.2	1
4153	1920-12-15	AMOS	QUE	709CEE9	-78.13	48.57	305	-0.6	-0.3	-0.3	1
4154	1920-12-28	AMOS	QUE	709CEE9	-78.13	48.57	305	-17.7	-17.1	-0.6	1
4155	1921-01-05	AMOS	QUE	709CEE9	-78.13	48.57	305	-10.6	-8.6	-2	1
4156	1921-01-08	AMOS	QUE	709CEE9	-78.13	48.57	305	-9.2	-9	-0.2	1
4157	1921-02-17	AMOS	QUE	709CEE9	-78.13	48.57	305	-12.8	-11.5	-1.3	1
4158	1921-03-03	AMOS	QUE	709CEE9	-78.13	48.57	305	-13.8	-13.1	-0.7	1
4159	1921-03-06	AMOS	QUE	709CEE9	-78.13	48.57	305	-8.7	-7.4	-1.3	1
4160	1921-03-21	AMOS	QUE	709CEE9	-78.13	48.57	305	-6.4	-4.8	-1.6	1
4161	1921-04-09	AMOS	QUE	709CEE9	-78.13	48.57	305	-7.6	-6.2	-1.4	1
4162	1921-04-15	AMOS	QUE	709CEE9	-78.13	48.57	305	-1.9	-0.3	-1.6	1
4163	1921-11-19	AMOS	QUE	709CEE9	-78.13	48.57	305	0	0.5	-0.5	1
4164	1921-12-05	AMOS	QUE	709CEE9	-78.13	48.57	305	-11.4	-9.8	-1.6	1
4165	1921-12-12	AMOS	QUE	709CEE9	-78.13	48.57	305	-11	-9.5	-1.5	1
4166	1921-12-13	AMOS	QUE	709CEE9	-78.13	48.57	305	-11.3	-11.2	-0.1	1
4167	1921-12-27	AMOS	QUE	709CEE9	-78.13	48.57	305	-10.1	-9.8	-0.3	1
4168	1922-02-03	AMOS	QUE	709CEE9	-78.13	48.57	305	-7	-5.2	-1.8	1
4169	1922-03-21	AMOS	QUE	709CEE9	-78.13	48.57	305	-8.7	-8	-0.7	1
4170	1922-10-23	AMOS	QUE	709CEE9	-78.13	48.57	305	0	0.3	-0.3	1
4171	1922-11-18	AMOS	QUE	709CEE9	-78.13	48.57	305	-1.8	-0.3	-1.5	1
4172	1922-11-20	AMOS	QUE	709CEE9	-78.13	48.57	305	-7	-6.5	-0.5	1
4173	1922-11-24	AMOS	QUE	709CEE9	-78.13	48.57	305	-7.6	-6.1	-1.5	1
4174	1922-12-12	AMOS	QUE	709CEE9	-78.13	48.57	305	-7	-5.3	-1.7	1
4175	1923-01-15	AMOS	QUE	709CEE9	-78.13	48.57	305	-9.2	-8	-1.2	1
4176	1923-03-03	AMOS	QUE	709CEE9	-78.13	48.57	305	-3	-1.4	-1.6	1
4177	1923-03-04	AMOS	QUE	709CEE9	-78.13	48.57	305	-10.9	-10.3	-0.6	1
4178	1923-10-05	AMOS	QUE	709CEE9	-78.13	48.57	305	5.4	5.7	-0.3	1
4179	1923-10-29	AMOS	QUE	709CEE9	-78.13	48.57	305	-4.7	-3.9	-0.8	1
4180	1923-11-04	AMOS	QUE	709CEE9	-78.13	48.57	305	0	0.1	-0.1	1
4181	1923-11-07	AMOS	QUE	709CEE9	-78.13	48.57	305	-3	-2	-1	1

4182	1923-11-27	AMOS	QUE	709CEE9	-78.13	48.57	305	-4.1	-3.9	-0.2	1
4183	1923-12-03	AMOS	QUE	709CEE9	-78.13	48.57	305	1.2	1.4	-0.2	1
4184	1923-12-21	AMOS	QUE	709CEE9	-78.13	48.57	305	-0.6	-0.3	-0.3	1
4185	1923-12-22	AMOS	QUE	709CEE9	-78.13	48.57	305	-3.6	-3.4	-0.2	1
4186	1924-01-04	AMOS	QUE	709CEE9	-78.13	48.57	305	-19.9	-18.9	-1	1
4187	1924-01-20	AMOS	QUE	709CEE9	-78.13	48.57	305	-21	-18.9	-2.1	1
4188	1924-11-04	AMOS	QUE	709CEE9	-78.13	48.57	305	-9.7	-8.9	-0.8	1
4189	1924-11-15	AMOS	QUE	709CEE9	-78.13	48.57	305	-5.8	-4.8	-1	1
4190	1924-11-16	AMOS	QUE	709CEE9	-78.13	48.57	305	-12.6	-12	-0.6	1
4191	1924-11-17	AMOS	QUE	709CEE9	-78.13	48.57	305	-12.6	-12.4	-0.2	1
4192	1924-11-22	AMOS	QUE	709CEE9	-78.13	48.57	305	2.9	4.1	-1.2	1
4193	1924-11-24	AMOS	QUE	709CEE9	-78.13	48.57	305	-5.2	-4.8	-0.4	1
4194	1924-11-25	AMOS	QUE	709CEE9	-78.13	48.57	305	-5.2	-4.4	-0.8	1
4195	1924-11-26	AMOS	QUE	709CEE9	-78.13	48.57	305	-1.9	-0.3	-1.6	1
4196	1924-12-04	AMOS	QUE	709CEE9	-78.13	48.57	305	-11.9	-10.7	-1.2	1
4197	1924-12-09	AMOS	QUE	709CEE9	-78.13	48.57	305	-9.7	-8.9	-0.8	1
4198	1924-12-17	AMOS	QUE	709CEE9	-78.13	48.57	305	-21	-20.8	-0.2	1
4199	1925-03-24	AMOS	QUE	709CEE9	-78.13	48.57	305	-0.6	0.1	-0.7	1
4200	1925-03-28	AMOS	QUE	709CEE9	-78.13	48.57	305	-1.9	-0.3	-1.6	1
4201	1925-03-29	AMOS	QUE	709CEE9	-78.13	48.57	305	-6.4	-4.8	-1.6	1
4202	1925-05-04	AMOS	QUE	709CEE9	-78.13	48.57	305	3.5	3.9	-0.4	1
4203	1925-11-14	AMOS	QUE	709CEE9	-78.13	48.57	305	-1.3	-0.3	-1	1
4204	1925-12-06	AMOS	QUE	709CEE9	-78.13	48.57	305	0	0.9	-0.9	1
4205	1925-12-07	AMOS	QUE	709CEE9	-78.13	48.57	305	-4.7	-4.4	-0.3	1
4206	1925-12-19	AMOS	QUE	709CEE9	-78.13	48.57	305	-14.3	-13.5	-0.8	1
4207	1926-01-12	AMOS	QUE	709CEE9	-78.13	48.57	305	-19.3	-19	-0.3	1
4208	1926-02-08	AMOS	QUE	709CEE9	-78.13	48.57	305	-23.8	-23.1	-0.7	1
4209	1926-04-25	AMOS	QUE	709CEE9	-78.13	48.57	305	-2.5	-2	-0.5	1
4210	1926-11-09	AMOS	QUE	709CEE9	-78.13	48.57	305	-4.7	-3.1	-1.6	1
4211	1926-11-10	AMOS	QUE	709CEE9	-78.13	48.57	305	-7.6	-7.5	-0.1	1
4212	1926-11-17	AMOS	QUE	709CEE9	-78.13	48.57	305	0	0.4	-0.4	1
4213	1926-11-18	AMOS	QUE	709CEE9	-78.13	48.57	305	-6.4	-4.8	-1.6	1
4214	1926-11-20	AMOS	QUE	709CEE9	-78.13	48.57	305	-6.9	-5.2	-1.7	1
4215	1926-11-27	AMOS	QUE	709CEE9	-78.13	48.57	305	-17.2	-17.1	-0.1	1

4216	1926-12-01	AMOS	QUE	709CEE9	-78.13	48.57	305	-12.8	-11.8	-1	1
4217	1926-12-14	AMOS	QUE	709CEE9	-78.13	48.57	305	-9.8	-8.5	-1.3	1
4218	1927-01-05	AMOS	QUE	709CEE9	-78.13	48.57	305	-11.7	-9.8	-1.9	1
4219	1927-01-13	AMOS	QUE	709CEE9	-78.13	48.57	305	-16.6	-15.7	-0.9	1
4220	1927-01-14	AMOS	QUE	709CEE9	-78.13	48.57	305	-18.8	-18.5	-0.3	1
4221	1927-09-22	AMOS	QUE	709CEE9	-78.13	48.57	305	2.3	6.2	-3.9	1
4222	1928-12-09	AMOS	QUE	709CEE9	-78.13	48.57	305	-11.5	-10.7	-0.8	1
4223	1929-02-25	AMOS	QUE	709CEE9	-78.13	48.57	305	-10.2	-4	-6.2	1
4224	1930-04-23	AMOS	QUE	709CEE9	-78.13	48.57	305	-9.2	-8.9	-0.3	1
4225	1930-10-21	AMOS	QUE	709CEE9	-78.13	48.57	305	-4.1	-4	-0.1	1
4226	1930-10-24	AMOS	QUE	709CEE9	-78.13	48.57	305	-3	-2.5	-0.5	1
4227	1930-10-29	AMOS	QUE	709CEE9	-78.13	48.57	305	1.2	3.1	-1.9	1
4228	1930-10-30	AMOS	QUE	709CEE9	-78.13	48.57	305	0	0.1	-0.1	1
4229	1930-11-03	AMOS	QUE	709CEE9	-78.13	48.57	305	0.5	0.9	-0.4	1
4230	1930-11-05	AMOS	QUE	709CEE9	-78.13	48.57	305	-3	-2.5	-0.5	1
4231	1930-11-09	AMOS	QUE	709CEE9	-78.13	48.57	305	-0.6	0.1	-0.7	1
4232	1931-04-25	AMOS	QUE	709CEE9	-78.13	48.57	305	3.5	4.8	-1.3	1
4233	1931-11-06	AMOS	QUE	709CEE9	-78.13	48.57	305	-5.8	-5.3	-0.5	1
4234	1931-12-04	AMOS	QUE	709CEE9	-78.13	48.57	305	-9.2	-8.6	-0.6	1
4235	1931-12-09	AMOS	QUE	709CEE9	-78.13	48.57	305	-5.8	-4.8	-1	1
4236	1931-12-10	AMOS	QUE	709CEE9	-78.13	48.57	305	-3.6	-3	-0.6	1
4237	1931-12-19	AMOS	QUE	709CEE9	-78.13	48.57	305	-20.4	-19.4	-1	1
4238	1932-01-07	AMOS	QUE	709CEE9	-78.13	48.57	305	-3.6	-2.5	-1.1	1
4239	1932-01-15	AMOS	QUE	709CEE9	-78.13	48.57	305	-5.8	-4.8	-1	1
4240	1932-01-18	AMOS	QUE	709CEE9	-78.13	48.57	305	-10.6	-8.5	-2.1	1
4241	1932-01-23	AMOS	QUE	709CEE9	-78.13	48.57	305	-14.6	-14	-0.6	1
4242	1932-01-31	AMOS	QUE	709CEE9	-78.13	48.57	305	-21	-20.3	-0.7	1
4243	1932-02-17	AMOS	QUE	709CEE9	-78.13	48.57	305	-5.8	-4.8	-1	1
4244	1932-03-09	AMOS	QUE	709CEE9	-78.13	48.57	305	-16.6	-16.2	-0.4	1
4245	1932-04-12	AMOS	QUE	709CEE9	-78.13	48.57	305	-6.4	-5.2	-1.2	1
4246	1932-11-02	AMOS	QUE	709CEE9	-78.13	48.57	305	-7	-4.8	-2.2	1
4247	1932-11-07	AMOS	QUE	709CEE9	-78.13	48.57	305	0.5	0.8	-0.3	1
4248	1933-03-09	AMOS	QUE	709CEE9	-78.13	48.57	305	-9.2	-6.6	-2.6	1
4249	1933-10-24	AMOS	QUE	709CEE9	-78.13	48.57	305	-4.7	-4	-0.7	1

4250	1933-10-25	AMOS	QUE	709CEE9	-78.13	48.57	305	-6.4	-5.2	-1.2	1
4251	1933-11-04	AMOS	QUE	709CEE9	-78.13	48.57	305	-6.4	-5.6	-0.8	1
4252	1933-11-10	AMOS	QUE	709CEE9	-78.13	48.57	305	-9.2	-8.9	-0.3	1
4253	1933-11-15	AMOS	QUE	709CEE9	-78.13	48.57	305	-13.2	-12	-1.2	1
4254	1933-12-03	AMOS	QUE	709CEE9	-78.13	48.57	305	-11	-10.4	-0.6	1
4255	1933-12-08	AMOS	QUE	709CEE9	-78.13	48.57	305	-21	-19.8	-1.2	1
4256	1934-01-06	AMOS	QUE	709CEE9	-78.13	48.57	305	-10.1	-9.9	-0.2	1
4257	1934-09-29	AMOS	QUE	709CEE9	-78.13	48.57	305	4.1	5.4	-1.3	1
4258	1934-10-28	AMOS	QUE	709CEE9	-78.13	48.57	305	-4.7	-3.9	-0.8	1
4259	1934-12-13	AMOS	QUE	709CEE9	-78.13	48.57	305	-12	-10.7	-1.3	1
4260	1935-01-11	AMOS	QUE	709CEE9	-78.13	48.57	305	-18.8	-18.5	-0.3	1
4261	1935-02-03	AMOS	QUE	709CEE9	-78.13	48.57	305	-12	-11.6	-0.4	1
4262	1935-03-17	AMOS	QUE	709CEE9	-78.13	48.57	305	-9.2	-7.5	-1.7	1
4263	1935-11-05	AMOS	QUE	709CEE9	-78.13	48.57	305	-2.5	-1.9	-0.6	1
4264	1935-12-18	AMOS	QUE	709CEE9	-78.13	48.57	305	-5.8	-5.2	-0.6	1
4265	1936-01-05	AMOS	QUE	709CEE9	-78.13	48.57	305	-6.4	-5.1	-1.3	1
4266	1936-10-17	AMOS	QUE	709CEE9	-78.13	48.57	305	5.5	5.6	-0.1	1
4267	1936-12-11	AMOS	QUE	709CEE9	-78.13	48.57	305	-11.9	-11.7	-0.2	1
4268	1937-02-26	AMOS	QUE	709CEE9	-78.13	48.57	305	-7.6	-7.5	-0.1	1
4269	1937-10-12	AMOS	QUE	709CEE9	-78.13	48.57	305	4.1	4.7	-0.6	1
4270	1937-11-09	AMOS	QUE	709CEE9	-78.13	48.57	305	-1.9	-1.3	-0.6	1
4271	1937-11-17	AMOS	QUE	709CEE9	-78.13	48.57	305	-4.1	-3.7	-0.4	1
4272	1937-12-06	AMOS	QUE	709CEE9	-78.13	48.57	305	-5.2	-4.1	-1.1	1
4273	1937-12-07	AMOS	QUE	709CEE9	-78.13	48.57	305	-7.6	-6.5	-1.1	1
4274	1938-04-01	AMOS	QUE	709CEE9	-78.13	48.57	305	-1.9	-1.3	-0.6	1
4275	1938-12-06	AMOS	QUE	709CEE9	-78.13	48.57	305	0.5	0.8	-0.3	1
4276	1939-11-08	AMOS	QUE	709CEE9	-78.13	48.57	305	-1.3	-0.7	-0.6	1
4277	1939-12-03	AMOS	QUE	709CEE9	-78.13	48.57	305	-4.7	-4.1	-0.6	1
4278	1941-12-06	AMOS	QUE	709CEE9	-78.13	48.57	305	-10.2	-9.1	-1.1	1
4279	1942-01-07	AMOS	QUE	709CEE9	-78.13	48.57	305	-30.4	-29.6	-0.8	1
4280	1942-01-18	AMOS	QUE	709CEE9	-78.13	48.57	305	-6.4	-5.6	-0.8	1
4281	1942-01-24	AMOS	QUE	709CEE9	-78.13	48.57	305	-10.5	-9.1	-1.4	1
4282	1943-01-01	AMOS	QUE	709CEE9	-78.13	48.57	305	-27.7	-27	-0.7	1
4283	1943-11-26	AMOS	QUE	709CEE9	-78.13	48.57	305	-1.9	-1.3	-0.6	1

4284	1944-01-10	AMOS	QUE	709CEE9	-78.13	48.57	305	-10.1	-8.6	-1.5	1
4285	1944-10-28	AMOS	QUE	709CEE9	-78.13	48.57	305	-0.7	-0.6	-0.1	1
4286	1946-01-12	AMOS	QUE	709CEE9	-78.13	48.57	305	-8.7	-7.5	-1.2	1
4287	1946-12-08	AMOS	QUE	709CEE9	-78.13	48.57	305	-4.7	-3.7	-1	1
4288	1950-10-20	AMOS	QUE	709CEE9	-78.13	48.57	305	-0.7	0.2	-0.9	1
4289	1951-04-03	AMOS	QUE	709CEE9	-78.13	48.57	305	0	0.1	-0.1	1
4290	1952-03-04	AMOS	QUE	709CEE9	-78.13	48.57	305	-8.6	-7.1	-1.5	1
4291	1952-03-05	AMOS	QUE	709CEE9	-78.13	48.57	305	-11.1	-10.5	-0.6	1
4292	1952-03-21	AMOS	QUE	709CEE9	-78.13	48.57	305	0.2	1	-0.8	1
4293	1952-04-14	AMOS	QUE	709CEE9	-78.13	48.57	305	-1.2	-0.2	-1	1
4294	1952-05-12	AMOS	QUE	709CEE9	-78.13	48.57	305	6.9	8.1	-1.2	1
4295	1952-05-25	AMOS	QUE	709CEE9	-78.13	48.57	305	11.1	13.7	-2.6	1
4296	1952-11-12	AMOS	QUE	709CEE9	-78.13	48.57	305	-4.7	-4.5	-0.2	1
4297	1952-12-25	AMOS	QUE	709CEE9	-78.13	48.57	305	-8.5	-7.6	-0.9	1
4298	1953-02-21	AMOS	QUE	709CEE9	-78.13	48.57	305	0.2	1.6	-1.4	1
4299	1953-03-05	AMOS	QUE	709CEE9	-78.13	48.57	305	-10	-8.8	-1.2	1
4300	1953-03-28	AMOS	QUE	709CEE9	-78.13	48.57	305	0.2	1	-0.8	1
4301	1953-09-12	AMOS	QUE	709CEE9	-78.13	48.57	305	11.6	12.1	-0.5	1
4302	1953-09-13	AMOS	QUE	709CEE9	-78.13	48.57	305	5.6	6.3	-0.7	1
4303	1953-11-15	AMOS	QUE	709CEE9	-78.13	48.57	305	0.8	1	-0.2	1
4304	1953-11-23	AMOS	QUE	709CEE9	-78.13	48.57	305	4	5.2	-1.2	1
4305	1953-11-26	AMOS	QUE	709CEE9	-78.13	48.57	305	-2.4	-1.2	-1.2	1
4306	1954-01-05	AMOS	QUE	709CEE9	-78.13	48.57	305	-13.6	-11.7	-1.9	1
4307	1954-02-03	AMOS	QUE	709CEE9	-78.13	48.57	305	-7.5	-6.5	-1	1
4308	1954-02-05	AMOS	QUE	709CEE9	-78.13	48.57	305	-11.1	-10.5	-0.6	1
4309	1954-11-24	AMOS	QUE	709CEE9	-78.13	48.57	305	-5.8	-5.5	-0.3	1
4310	1954-11-26	AMOS	QUE	709CEE9	-78.13	48.57	305	-3	-1.8	-1.2	1
4311	1954-11-30	AMOS	QUE	709CEE9	-78.13	48.57	305	-6.9	-5.5	-1.4	1
4312	1955-04-06	AMOS	QUE	709CEE9	-78.13	48.57	305	-1.1	1	-2.1	1
4313	1956-01-31	AMOS	QUE	709CEE9	-78.13	48.57	305	-13.6	-12.8	-0.8	1
4314	1956-04-14	AMOS	QUE	709CEE9	-78.13	48.57	305	-4.1	-3.1	-1	1
4315	1956-08-10	AMOS	QUE	709CEE9	-78.13	48.57	305	12.8	16.5	-3.7	1
4316	1956-09-29	AMOS	QUE	709CEE9	-78.13	48.57	305	6.5	7.4	-0.9	1
4317	1956-11-07	AMOS	QUE	709CEE9	-78.13	48.57	305	9.7	10.4	-0.7	1

4318	1957-06-23	AMOS	QUE	709CEE9	-78.13	48.57	305	19.5	19.8	-0.3	1
4319	1957-06-30	AMOS	QUE	709CEE9	-78.13	48.57	305	10.2	10.4	-0.2	1
4320	1958-02-08	AMOS	QUE	709CEE9	-78.13	48.57	305	-19	-18.1	-0.9	1
4321	1958-02-09	AMOS	QUE	709CEE9	-78.13	48.57	305	-20.6	-19.9	-0.7	1
4322	1958-12-16	AMOS	QUE	709CEE9	-78.13	48.57	305	-24.5	-22.6	-1.9	1
4323	1958-12-19	AMOS	QUE	709CEE9	-78.13	48.57	305	-24.5	-23.8	-0.7	1
4324	1958-12-23	AMOS	QUE	709CEE9	-78.13	48.57	305	-16.3	-14.5	-1.8	1
4325	1959-01-16	AMOS	QUE	709CEE9	-78.13	48.57	305	-17.4	-16.1	-1.3	1
4326	1959-02-06	AMOS	QUE	709CEE9	-78.13	48.57	305	-25.6	-23.9	-1.7	1
4327	1959-03-04	AMOS	QUE	709CEE9	-78.13	48.57	305	-3.6	-3.1	-0.5	1
4328	1959-03-21	AMOS	QUE	709CEE9	-78.13	48.57	305	-12.6	-10.5	-2.1	1
4329	1959-03-26	AMOS	QUE	709CEE9	-78.13	48.57	305	-8.6	-7.6	-1	1
4330	1959-06-29	AMOS	QUE	709CEE9	-78.13	48.57	305	18.5	20.4	-1.9	1
4331	1959-10-25	AMOS	QUE	709CEE9	-78.13	48.57	305	1.5	1.6	-0.1	1
4332	1959-11-02	AMOS	QUE	709CEE9	-78.13	48.57	305	-6.9	-6	-0.9	1
4333	1959-11-24	AMOS	QUE	709CEE9	-78.13	48.57	305	-7.5	-7.1	-0.4	1
4334	1959-11-25	AMOS	QUE	709CEE9	-78.13	48.57	305	-11.1	-10.5	-0.6	1
4335	1959-11-26	AMOS	QUE	709CEE9	-78.13	48.57	305	-11.6	-10.5	-1.1	1
4336	1959-12-05	AMOS	QUE	709CEE9	-78.13	48.57	305	-0.6	1	-1.6	1
4337	1959-12-16	AMOS	QUE	709CEE9	-78.13	48.57	305	-1.1	-0.2	-0.9	1
4338	1960-04-17	AMOS	QUE	709CEE9	-78.13	48.57	305	-3	-1.3	-1.7	1
4339	1960-06-29	AMOS	QUE	709CEE9	-78.13	48.57	305	14.6	15.4	-0.8	1
4340	1960-11-04	AMOS	QUE	709CEE9	-78.13	48.57	305	-1.8	-0.2	-1.6	1
4341	1960-11-18	AMOS	QUE	709CEE9	-78.13	48.57	305	-3	-1.8	-1.2	1
4342	1960-12-16	AMOS	QUE	709CEE9	-78.13	48.57	305	-12.2	-10.5	-1.7	1
4343	1961-01-11	AMOS	QUE	709CEE9	-78.13	48.57	305	-12.6	-9.4	-3.2	1
4344	1961-02-22	AMOS	QUE	709CEE9	-78.13	48.57	305	-8.6	-8.2	-0.4	1
4345	1961-03-24	AMOS	QUE	709CEE9	-78.13	48.57	305	-1.8	-0.2	-1.6	1
4346	1961-05-02	AMOS	QUE	709CEE9	-78.13	48.57	305	2.8	2.9	-0.1	1
4347	1961-05-20	AMOS	QUE	709CEE9	-78.13	48.57	305	8.6	9.8	-1.2	1
4348	1961-10-25	AMOS	QUE	709CEE9	-78.13	48.57	305	0.8	4.6	-3.8	1
4349	1961-11-07	AMOS	QUE	709CEE9	-78.13	48.57	305	-3	-2.7	-0.3	1
4350	1961-11-08	AMOS	QUE	709CEE9	-78.13	48.57	305	-5.8	-5.1	-0.7	1
4351	1961-11-15	AMOS	QUE	709CEE9	-78.13	48.57	305	-2.4	-1.2	-1.2	1

4352	1961-11-16	AMOS	QUE	709CEE9	-78.13	48.57	305	-4.1	-1.2	-2.9	1
4353	1961-11-24	AMOS	QUE	709CEE9	-78.13	48.57	305	-3	-1.8	-1.2	1
4354	1961-11-25	AMOS	QUE	709CEE9	-78.13	48.57	305	-7.5	-5.1	-2.4	1
4355	1961-11-26	AMOS	QUE	709CEE9	-78.13	48.57	305	-9.6	-2.7	-6.9	1
4356	1961-11-27	AMOS	QUE	709CEE9	-78.13	48.57	305	-9.6	-4.2	-5.4	1
4357	1961-12-19	AMOS	QUE	709CEE9	-78.13	48.57	305	-9.6	-9.3	-0.3	1
4358	1962-01-08	AMOS	QUE	709CEE9	-78.13	48.57	305	-16.3	-16.1	-0.2	1
4359	1962-02-28	AMOS	QUE	709CEE9	-78.13	48.57	305	-13.6	-11.7	-1.9	1
4360	2009-12-27	AMOS	QUE	709CEE9	-78.13	48.57	305	-4	-2.5	-1.5	1
4361	1913-11-24	TEMISCAMINGUE	QUE	7080468	-79.1	46.72	181	-1.3	-1.1	-0.2	1
4362	1913-11-26	TEMISCAMINGUE	QUE	7080468	-79.1	46.72	181	-2.8	-2.2	-0.6	1
4363	1914-08-27	TEMISCAMINGUE	QUE	7080468	-79.1	46.72	181	23.5	23.9	-0.4	1
4364	1914-09-01	TEMISCAMINGUE	QUE	7080468	-79.1	46.72	181	20.5	20.6	-0.1	1
4365	1914-12-03	TEMISCAMINGUE	QUE	7080468	-79.1	46.72	181	-3.5	-3.3	-0.2	1
4366	1914-12-13	TEMISCAMINGUE	QUE	7080468	-79.1	46.72	181	-3.5	-2.8	-0.7	1
4367	1915-01-11	TEMISCAMINGUE	QUE	7080468	-79.1	46.72	181	-5.4	-5	-0.4	1
4368	1915-01-15	TEMISCAMINGUE	QUE	7080468	-79.1	46.72	181	-6.3	-5.6	-0.7	1
4369	1915-01-18	TEMISCAMINGUE	QUE	7080468	-79.1	46.72	181	-4	-2.2	-1.8	1
4370	1915-03-20	TEMISCAMINGUE	QUE	7080468	-79.1	46.72	181	-4	-2.8	-1.2	1
4371	1915-06-14	TEMISCAMINGUE	QUE	7080468	-79.1	46.72	181	16.3	16.7	-0.4	1
4372	1915-08-06	TEMISCAMINGUE	QUE	7080468	-79.1	46.72	181	15.8	16.7	-0.9	1
4373	1915-08-13	TEMISCAMINGUE	QUE	7080468	-79.1	46.72	181	16.8	17.2	-0.4	1
4374	1915-10-15	TEMISCAMINGUE	QUE	7080468	-79.1	46.72	181	4.3	5	-0.7	1
4375	1916-01-05	TEMISCAMINGUE	QUE	7080468	-79.1	46.72	181	-4.6	-2.8	-1.8	1
4376	1916-01-22	TEMISCAMINGUE	QUE	7080468	-79.1	46.72	181	-0.9	0	-0.9	1
4377	1916-01-25	TEMISCAMINGUE	QUE	7080468	-79.1	46.72	181	0.7	1.1	-0.4	1
4378	1916-01-27	TEMISCAMINGUE	QUE	7080468	-79.1	46.72	181	-7.3	-6.7	-0.6	1
4379	1916-03-27	TEMISCAMINGUE	QUE	7080468	-79.1	46.72	181	-0.1	0.6	-0.7	1
4380	1916-04-01	TEMISCAMINGUE	QUE	7080468	-79.1	46.72	181	3.4	3.9	-0.5	1
4381	1916-04-17	TEMISCAMINGUE	QUE	7080468	-79.1	46.72	181	5	5.6	-0.6	1
4382	1916-06-14	TEMISCAMINGUE	QUE	7080468	-79.1	46.72	181	15.9	17.2	-1.3	1
4383	1916-06-15	TEMISCAMINGUE	QUE	7080468	-79.1	46.72	181	15.6	16.1	-0.5	1
4384	1916-07-13	TEMISCAMINGUE	QUE	7080468	-79.1	46.72	181	18.7	19.4	-0.7	1
4385	1916-07-20	TEMISCAMINGUE	QUE	7080468	-79.1	46.72	181	21	22.8	-1.8	1

4386	1916-08-07	TEMISCAMINGUE	QUE	7080468	-79.1	46.72	181	19.3	19.4	-0.1	1
4387	1916-09-29	TEMISCAMINGUE	QUE	7080468	-79.1	46.72	181	1.9	2.2	-0.3	1
4388	1916-10-09	TEMISCAMINGUE	QUE	7080468	-79.1	46.72	181	-0.9	0	-0.9	1
4389	1916-10-13	TEMISCAMINGUE	QUE	7080468	-79.1	46.72	181	3	3.3	-0.3	1
4390	1916-10-28	TEMISCAMINGUE	QUE	7080468	-79.1	46.72	181	-1.2	-1.1	-0.1	1
4391	1916-12-04	TEMISCAMINGUE	QUE	7080468	-79.1	46.72	181	-0.1	0	-0.1	1
4392	1917-08-09	TEMISCAMINGUE	QUE	7080468	-79.1	46.72	181	21	24.4	-3.4	1
4393	1917-08-13	TEMISCAMINGUE	QUE	7080468	-79.1	46.72	181	17.7	20	-2.3	1
4394	1917-10-01	TEMISCAMINGUE	QUE	7080468	-79.1	46.72	181	3.7	4.4	-0.7	1
4395	1917-10-04	TEMISCAMINGUE	QUE	7080468	-79.1	46.72	181	3.7	3.9	-0.2	1
4396	1917-10-27	TEMISCAMINGUE	QUE	7080468	-79.1	46.72	181	5	5.6	-0.6	1
4397	1917-12-04	TEMISCAMINGUE	QUE	7080468	-79.1	46.72	181	-4.6	-4.4	-0.2	1
4398	1918-08-10	TEMISCAMINGUE	QUE	7080468	-79.1	46.72	181	21.1	21.7	-0.6	1
4399	1918-08-13	TEMISCAMINGUE	QUE	7080468	-79.1	46.72	181	28	28.9	-0.9	1
4400	1918-11-27	TEMISCAMINGUE	QUE	7080468	-79.1	46.72	181	-2.7	-2.2	-0.5	1
4401	1918-12-16	TEMISCAMINGUE	QUE	7080468	-79.1	46.72	181	-4.1	-3.9	-0.2	1
4402	1919-07-31	TEMISCAMINGUE	QUE	7080468	-79.1	46.72	181	17.7	19.4	-1.7	1
4403	1920-02-07	TEMISCAMINGUE	QUE	7080468	-79.1	46.72	181	-4.1	-3.9	-0.2	1
4404	1921-03-11	TEMISCAMINGUE	QUE	7080468	-79.1	46.72	181	-2.7	-2.2	-0.5	1
4405	1922-01-05	TEMISCAMINGUE	QUE	7080468	-79.1	46.72	181	-11.2	-10.6	-0.6	1
4406	1922-01-10	TEMISCAMINGUE	QUE	7080468	-79.1	46.72	181	-8.6	-7.2	-1.4	1
4407	1922-10-12	TEMISCAMINGUE	QUE	7080468	-79.1	46.72	181	9.3	9.4	-0.1	1
4408	1922-10-19	TEMISCAMINGUE	QUE	7080468	-79.1	46.72	181	16.5	16.7	-0.2	1
4409	1922-11-05	TEMISCAMINGUE	QUE	7080468	-79.1	46.72	181	5.2	6.1	-0.9	1
4410	1922-11-20	TEMISCAMINGUE	QUE	7080468	-79.1	46.72	181	-4.9	-4.4	-0.5	1
4411	1922-11-21	TEMISCAMINGUE	QUE	7080468	-79.1	46.72	181	-6.7	-6.1	-0.6	1
4412	1922-11-25	TEMISCAMINGUE	QUE	7080468	-79.1	46.72	181	-8.2	-7.8	-0.4	1
4413	1922-11-28	TEMISCAMINGUE	QUE	7080468	-79.1	46.72	181	-8.2	-7.2	-1	1
4414	1923-10-30	TEMISCAMINGUE	QUE	7080468	-79.1	46.72	181	-1.4	-1.1	-0.3	1
4415	1923-11-06	TEMISCAMINGUE	QUE	7080468	-79.1	46.72	181	5.1	6.1	-1	1
4416	1923-12-01	TEMISCAMINGUE	QUE	7080468	-79.1	46.72	181	0.7	1.7	-1	1
4417	1923-12-04	TEMISCAMINGUE	QUE	7080468	-79.1	46.72	181	0.5	1.1	-0.6	1
4418	1923-12-05	TEMISCAMINGUE	QUE	7080468	-79.1	46.72	181	0.7	1.1	-0.4	1
4419	1923-12-06	TEMISCAMINGUE	QUE	7080468	-79.1	46.72	181	0.7	1.1	-0.4	1

4420	1923-12-16	TEMISCAMINGUE	QUE	7080468	-79.1	46.72	181	0.5	0.6	-0.1	1
4421	1924-01-19	TEMISCAMINGUE	QUE	7080468	-79.1	46.72	181	-6.7	-5.6	-1.1	1
4422	1924-02-11	TEMISCAMINGUE	QUE	7080468	-79.1	46.72	181	-8.4	-6.7	-1.7	1
4423	1924-02-17	TEMISCAMINGUE	QUE	7080468	-79.1	46.72	181	-8.5	-6.7	-1.8	1
4424	1924-03-05	TEMISCAMINGUE	QUE	7080468	-79.1	46.72	181	-0.4	0.6	-1	1
4425	1924-03-31	TEMISCAMINGUE	QUE	7080468	-79.1	46.72	181	-8.5	-8.3	-0.2	1
4426	1924-04-18	TEMISCAMINGUE	QUE	7080468	-79.1	46.72	181	1.1	3.3	-2.2	1
4427	1924-04-22	TEMISCAMINGUE	QUE	7080468	-79.1	46.72	181	0	0.6	-0.6	1
4428	1924-05-10	TEMISCAMINGUE	QUE	7080468	-79.1	46.72	181	8	8.9	-0.9	1
4429	1924-05-24	TEMISCAMINGUE	QUE	7080468	-79.1	46.72	181	6.6	6.7	-0.1	1
4430	1924-06-29	TEMISCAMINGUE	QUE	7080468	-79.1	46.72	181	11.4	11.7	-0.3	1
4431	1924-07-13	TEMISCAMINGUE	QUE	7080468	-79.1	46.72	181	14	14.4	-0.4	1
4432	1924-07-30	TEMISCAMINGUE	QUE	7080468	-79.1	46.72	181	17.6	17.8	-0.2	1
4433	1924-09-06	TEMISCAMINGUE	QUE	7080468	-79.1	46.72	181	5.8	7.2	-1.4	1
4434	1924-09-10	TEMISCAMINGUE	QUE	7080468	-79.1	46.72	181	5.2	5.6	-0.4	1
4435	1924-10-07	TEMISCAMINGUE	QUE	7080468	-79.1	46.72	181	5.9	6.7	-0.8	1
4436	1925-02-05	TEMISCAMINGUE	QUE	7080468	-79.1	46.72	181	0.2	0.6	-0.4	1
4437	1925-03-28	TEMISCAMINGUE	QUE	7080468	-79.1	46.72	181	-2.9	-2.8	-0.1	1
4438	1925-10-08	TEMISCAMINGUE	QUE	7080468	-79.1	46.72	181	0.7	2.2	-1.5	1
4439	1925-10-25	TEMISCAMINGUE	QUE	7080468	-79.1	46.72	181	-0.3	0	-0.3	1
4440	1925-11-08	TEMISCAMINGUE	QUE	7080468	-79.1	46.72	181	-3.6	-3.3	-0.3	1
4441	1925-11-13	TEMISCAMINGUE	QUE	7080468	-79.1	46.72	181	2.3	2.8	-0.5	1
4442	1925-11-14	TEMISCAMINGUE	QUE	7080468	-79.1	46.72	181	1.1	1.7	-0.6	1
4443	1925-11-15	TEMISCAMINGUE	QUE	7080468	-79.1	46.72	181	0.8	1.7	-0.9	1
4444	1925-11-16	TEMISCAMINGUE	QUE	7080468	-79.1	46.72	181	-2.8	-2.2	-0.6	1
4445	1925-11-19	TEMISCAMINGUE	QUE	7080468	-79.1	46.72	181	2.3	2.8	-0.5	1
4446	1925-11-20	TEMISCAMINGUE	QUE	7080468	-79.1	46.72	181	0.8	1.7	-0.9	1
4447	1925-11-22	TEMISCAMINGUE	QUE	7080468	-79.1	46.72	181	-5.5	-3.9	-1.6	1
4448	1925-11-25	TEMISCAMINGUE	QUE	7080468	-79.1	46.72	181	-6.2	-4.4	-1.8	1
4449	1925-12-05	TEMISCAMINGUE	QUE	7080468	-79.1	46.72	181	3.8	3.9	-0.1	1
4450	1925-12-06	TEMISCAMINGUE	QUE	7080468	-79.1	46.72	181	-1.5	-0.6	-0.9	1
4451	1925-12-14	TEMISCAMINGUE	QUE	7080468	-79.1	46.72	181	-9.3	-8.9	-0.4	1
4452	1925-12-21	TEMISCAMINGUE	QUE	7080468	-79.1	46.72	181	-8.2	-6.7	-1.5	1
4453	1926-01-06	TEMISCAMINGUE	QUE	7080468	-79.1	46.72	181	-3.5	-2.2	-1.3	1

4454	1926-01-19	TEMISCAMINGUE	QUE	7080468	-79.1	46.72	181	-9.7	-9.4	-0.3	1
4455	1926-01-28	TEMISCAMINGUE	QUE	7080468	-79.1	46.72	181	-11.3	-11.1	-0.2	1
4456	1926-04-25	TEMISCAMINGUE	QUE	7080468	-79.1	46.72	181	-3.6	-3.3	-0.3	1
4457	1926-05-02	TEMISCAMINGUE	QUE	7080468	-79.1	46.72	181	2.3	2.8	-0.5	1
4458	1926-05-03	TEMISCAMINGUE	QUE	7080468	-79.1	46.72	181	-4.2	-3.9	-0.3	1
4459	1926-05-22	TEMISCAMINGUE	QUE	7080468	-79.1	46.72	181	1.7	2.2	-0.5	1
4460	1926-09-25	TEMISCAMINGUE	QUE	7080468	-79.1	46.72	181	5.8	6.1	-0.3	1
4461	1926-10-25	TEMISCAMINGUE	QUE	7080468	-79.1	46.72	181	0.1	1.1	-1	1
4462	1926-11-03	TEMISCAMINGUE	QUE	7080468	-79.1	46.72	181	-2.9	-2.8	-0.1	1
4463	1926-11-09	TEMISCAMINGUE	QUE	7080468	-79.1	46.72	181	-1.4	-1.1	-0.3	1
4464	1926-11-10	TEMISCAMINGUE	QUE	7080468	-79.1	46.72	181	-7.3	-6.7	-0.6	1
4465	1926-11-16	TEMISCAMINGUE	QUE	7080468	-79.1	46.72	181	3	4.4	-1.4	1
4466	1926-11-17	TEMISCAMINGUE	QUE	7080468	-79.1	46.72	181	0.7	1.7	-1	1
4467	1926-11-19	TEMISCAMINGUE	QUE	7080468	-79.1	46.72	181	-0.3	0.6	-0.9	1
4468	1926-11-20	TEMISCAMINGUE	QUE	7080468	-79.1	46.72	181	-6.7	-5	-1.7	1
4469	1926-11-21	TEMISCAMINGUE	QUE	7080468	-79.1	46.72	181	-8.1	-7.8	-0.3	1
4470	1926-11-24	TEMISCAMINGUE	QUE	7080468	-79.1	46.72	181	-8.4	-7.2	-1.2	1
4471	1926-12-14	TEMISCAMINGUE	QUE	7080468	-79.1	46.72	181	-8.2	-6.7	-1.5	1
4472	2008-10-13	QUATSINO	BC	1036572	-127.65	50.53	21	8.5	10	-1.5	1
4473	2016-04-23	QUATSINO	BC	1036572	-127.65	50.53	21	9	10	-1	1
4474	1987-01-20	DANIELS HARBOUR	NFLD	8401400	-57.58	50.23	19	-25.8	-15.6	-10.2	1
4475	1987-11-29	DANIELS HARBOUR	NFLD	8401400	-57.58	50.23	19	-1.8	-0.2	-1.6	1
4476	1988-11-13	DANIELS HARBOUR	NFLD	8401400	-57.58	50.23	19	-4	-2.6	-1.4	1
4477	1995-03-19	DANIELS HARBOUR	NFLD	8401400	-57.58	50.23	19	-6.8	-6.5	-0.3	1
4478	2000-04-08	DANIELS HARBOUR	NFLD	8401400	-57.58	50.23	19	3.2	4	-0.8	1
4479	1903-01-08	DAUPHIN	MAN	5040689	-100.05	51.1	305	-18.5	-17.6	-0.9	1
4480	1903-02-13	DAUPHIN	MAN	5040689	-100.05	51.1	305	-20.4	-19.8	-0.6	1
4481	1903-02-27	DAUPHIN	MAN	5040689	-100.05	51.1	305	-11.6	-11.1	-0.5	1
4482	1903-11-28	DAUPHIN	MAN	5040689	-100.05	51.1	305	-6	-5.8	-0.2	1
4483	1903-12-03	DAUPHIN	MAN	5040689	-100.05	51.1	305	-13.7	-12.2	-1.5	1
4484	1904-11-25	DAUPHIN	MAN	5040689	-100.05	51.1	305	-8	-7.2	-0.8	1
4485	1904-11-27	DAUPHIN	MAN	5040689	-100.05	51.1	305	-9.3	-9.1	-0.2	1
4486	1904-12-10	DAUPHIN	MAN	5040689	-100.05	51.1	305	-11.6	-11.1	-0.5	1
4487	1904-12-15	DAUPHIN	MAN	5040689	-100.05	51.1	305	-9.3	-9.1	-0.2	1

4488	1904-12-20	DAUPHIN	MAN	5040689	-100.05	51.1	305	-10	-7.8	-2.2	1
4489	1905-03-08	DAUPHIN	MAN	5040689	-100.05	51.1	305	-13.2	-12.2	-1	1
4490	1905-06-13	DAUPHIN	MAN	5040689	-100.05	51.1	305	9.5	10.2	-0.7	1
4491	1905-06-23	DAUPHIN	MAN	5040689	-100.05	51.1	305	8.9	9.5	-0.6	1
4492	1905-09-30	DAUPHIN	MAN	5040689	-100.05	51.1	305	9.5	10.2	-0.7	1
4493	1905-10-10	DAUPHIN	MAN	5040689	-100.05	51.1	305	-1	-0.3	-0.7	1
4494	1905-11-26	DAUPHIN	MAN	5040689	-100.05	51.1	305	-7.9	-7.2	-0.7	1
4495	1905-11-28	DAUPHIN	MAN	5040689	-100.05	51.1	305	-17.6	-17.2	-0.4	1
4496	1905-12-12	DAUPHIN	MAN	5040689	-100.05	51.1	305	-14.8	-13.6	-1.2	1
4497	1905-12-22	DAUPHIN	MAN	5040689	-100.05	51.1	305	-15.4	-14.1	-1.3	1
4498	1905-12-30	DAUPHIN	MAN	5040689	-100.05	51.1	305	-16.1	-15.4	-0.7	1
4499	1905-12-31	DAUPHIN	MAN	5040689	-100.05	51.1	305	-15.7	-15.3	-0.4	1
4500	1906-04-04	DAUPHIN	MAN	5040689	-100.05	51.1	305	2.1	2.3	-0.2	1
4501	1906-11-16	DAUPHIN	MAN	5040689	-100.05	51.1	305	-7.3	-5.7	-1.6	1
4502	1906-11-30	DAUPHIN	MAN	5040689	-100.05	51.1	305	-15.8	-15.7	-0.1	1
4503	1907-05-12	DAUPHIN	MAN	5040689	-100.05	51.1	305	-1.8	-0.3	-1.5	1
4504	1907-09-11	DAUPHIN	MAN	5040689	-100.05	51.1	305	6.2	6.4	-0.2	1
4505	1907-11-09	DAUPHIN	MAN	5040689	-100.05	51.1	305	-6.7	-5.2	-1.5	1
4506	1907-11-27	DAUPHIN	MAN	5040689	-100.05	51.1	305	-10.5	-10.4	-0.1	1
4507	1912-12-22	DAUPHIN	MAN	5040689	-100.05	51.1	305	-9.3	-7.8	-1.5	1
4508	1914-12-04	DAUPHIN	MAN	5040689	-100.05	51.1	305	-8.6	-6.7	-1.9	1
4509	1914-12-05	DAUPHIN	MAN	5040689	-100.05	51.1	305	-7.4	-5.8	-1.6	1
4510	1914-12-06	DAUPHIN	MAN	5040689	-100.05	51.1	305	-7.4	-5.8	-1.6	1
4511	1914-12-07	DAUPHIN	MAN	5040689	-100.05	51.1	305	-6.1	-5.8	-0.3	1
4512	1914-12-17	DAUPHIN	MAN	5040689	-100.05	51.1	305	-13.9	-13.2	-0.7	1
4513	1915-01-06	DAUPHIN	MAN	5040689	-100.05	51.1	305	-7.4	-6.7	-0.7	1
4514	1915-01-29	DAUPHIN	MAN	5040689	-100.05	51.1	305	-30.2	-27	-3.2	1
4515	1915-03-02	DAUPHIN	MAN	5040689	-100.05	51.1	305	-10.5	-8.4	-2.1	1
4516	1918-10-30	DAUPHIN	MAN	5040689	-100.05	51.1	305	-1.1	-0.3	-0.8	1
4517	1919-12-06	DAUPHIN	MAN	5040689	-100.05	51.1	305	-16.3	-15.4	-0.9	1
4518	1929-05-24	DAUPHIN	MAN	5040689	-100.05	51.1	305	11.9	13.2	-1.3	1
4519	1934-10-16	DAUPHIN	MAN	5040689	-100.05	51.1	305	5.4	5.9	-0.5	1
4520	1935-10-08	DAUPHIN	MAN	5040689	-100.05	51.1	305	6.8	7.6	-0.8	1
4521	1936-06-16	DAUPHIN	MAN	5040689	-100.05	51.1	305	11.9	12	-0.1	1

4522	1936-11-20	DAUPHIN	MAN	5040689	-100.05	51.1	305	4.6	4.9	-0.3	1
4523	1938-10-04	DAUPHIN	MAN	5040689	-100.05	51.1	305	8.1	8.4	-0.3	1
4524	1939-08-07	DAUPHIN	MAN	5040689	-100.05	51.1	305	14.9	15.6	-0.7	1
4525	1939-09-24	DAUPHIN	MAN	5040689	-100.05	51.1	305	8.8	9.6	-0.8	1
4526	1940-05-13	DAUPHIN	MAN	5040689	-100.05	51.1	305	5	5.4	-0.4	1
4527	1940-10-04	DAUPHIN	MAN	5040689	-100.05	51.1	305	11.9	12	-0.1	1
4528	1981-02-24	GREAT FALLS	MAN	5031201	-96	50.47	253	-7	-3	-4	1
4529	2016-03-15	GREAT FALLS	MAN	5031201	-96	50.47	253	1.6	4.7	-3.1	1
4530	1920-12-25	EDMUNDSTON	NB	8101303	-68.18	47.33	154	-20.6	-19.4	-1.2	1
4531	1920-12-26	EDMUNDSTON	NB	8101303	-68.18	47.33	154	-18.9	-18.8	-0.1	1
4532	1984-10-16	LYNN LAKE	MAN	5061645	-101.08	56.87	357	0.9	2.8	-1.9	1
4533	1916-07-26	COLLEGEVILLE	NS	8201000	-62.02	45.48	76	23	25.8	-2.8	1
4534	1919-12-24	COLLEGEVILLE	NS	8201000	-62.02	45.48	76	-1.1	-0.7	-0.4	1
4535	1920-10-06	COLLEGEVILLE	NS	8201000	-62.02	45.48	76	9	9.3	-0.3	1
4536	1920-11-26	COLLEGEVILLE	NS	8201000	-62.02	45.48	76	1.5	2.3	-0.8	1
4537	1922-08-08	COLLEGEVILLE	NS	8201000	-62.02	45.48	76	19.5	19.7	-0.2	1
4538	1923-12-29	COLLEGEVILLE	NS	8201000	-62.02	45.48	76	-2.7	-2.5	-0.2	1
4539	1924-08-15	COLLEGEVILLE	NS	8201000	-62.02	45.48	76	15.1	15.4	-0.3	1
4540	1925-08-08	COLLEGEVILLE	NS	8201000	-62.02	45.48	76	16.6	16.9	-0.3	1
4541	1925-08-31	COLLEGEVILLE	NS	8201000	-62.02	45.48	76	18.4	18.6	-0.2	1
4542	1925-09-01	COLLEGEVILLE	NS	8201000	-62.02	45.48	76	16.2	16.9	-0.7	1
4543	1932-11-09	COLLEGEVILLE	NS	8201000	-62.02	45.48	76	3.8	4.4	-0.6	1
4544	1937-03-19	COLLEGEVILLE	NS	8201000	-62.02	45.48	76	2.7	3.9	-1.2	1
4545	1938-06-12	COLLEGEVILLE	NS	8201000	-62.02	45.48	76	10.6	11.1	-0.5	1
4546	1938-11-01	COLLEGEVILLE	NS	8201000	-62.02	45.48	76	4.9	5	-0.1	1
4547	1940-11-16	COLLEGEVILLE	NS	8201000	-62.02	45.48	76	3.8	3.9	-0.1	1
4548	1941-01-19	COLLEGEVILLE	NS	8201000	-62.02	45.48	76	2.9	3.3	-0.4	1
4549	1943-05-13	COLLEGEVILLE	NS	8201000	-62.02	45.48	76	8.4	8.9	-0.5	1
4550	1945-06-30	COLLEGEVILLE	NS	8201000	-62.02	45.48	76	9.5	11.1	-1.6	1
4551	1946-04-09	COLLEGEVILLE	NS	8201000	-62.02	45.48	76	2.7	2.8	-0.1	1
4552	1946-08-25	COLLEGEVILLE	NS	8201000	-62.02	45.48	76	19.5	20	-0.5	1
4553	2002-12-05	COLLEGEVILLE	NS	8201000	-62.02	45.48	76	-7	-6.5	-0.5	1
4554	2003-02-13	COLLEGEVILLE	NS	8201000	-62.02	45.48	76	-17	-16.5	-0.5	1
4555	2003-02-16	COLLEGEVILLE	NS	8201000	-62.02	45.48	76	-22	-18	-4	1

4556	2003-02-25	COLLEGEVILLE	NS	8201000	-62.02	45.48	76	-11	-10	-1	1
4557	2003-03-13	COLLEGEVILLE	NS	8201000	-62.02	45.48	76	-10	-8.5	-1.5	1
4558	2003-03-29	COLLEGEVILLE	NS	8201000	-62.02	45.48	76	9	10	-1	1
4559	2003-04-06	COLLEGEVILLE	NS	8201000	-62.02	45.48	76	-1	0	-1	1
4560	2004-02-24	COLLEGEVILLE	NS	8201000	-62.02	45.48	76	-5	-4.5	-0.5	1
4561	2006-12-11	COLLEGEVILLE	NS	8201000	-62.02	45.48	76	-8	-5	-3	1
4562	2006-12-28	COLLEGEVILLE	NS	8201000	-62.02	45.48	76	-5	-3	-2	1
4563	2007-03-24	COLLEGEVILLE	NS	8201000	-62.02	45.48	76	0	2	-2	1
4564	2007-12-17	COLLEGEVILLE	NS	8201000	-62.02	45.48	76	-7	-4	-3	1
4565	2008-02-02	COLLEGEVILLE	NS	8201000	-62.02	45.48	76	0	4	-4	1
4566	2008-02-03	COLLEGEVILLE	NS	8201000	-62.02	45.48	76	-8	-6	-2	1
4567	2008-02-11	COLLEGEVILLE	NS	8201000	-62.02	45.48	76	-4	0	-4	1
4568	2008-02-12	COLLEGEVILLE	NS	8201000	-62.02	45.48	76	-8	-6	-2	1
4569	2008-02-15	COLLEGEVILLE	NS	8201000	-62.02	45.48	76	-6	-2	-4	1
4570	2008-02-16	COLLEGEVILLE	NS	8201000	-62.02	45.48	76	-14	-10	-4	1
4571	2008-02-21	COLLEGEVILLE	NS	8201000	-62.02	45.48	76	-7	-6	-1	1
4572	2008-02-23	COLLEGEVILLE	NS	8201000	-62.02	45.48	76	-5	0	-5	1
4573	2008-02-24	COLLEGEVILLE	NS	8201000	-62.02	45.48	76	-6	-5	-1	1
4574	2008-03-02	COLLEGEVILLE	NS	8201000	-62.02	45.48	76	-1	0	-1	1
4575	2008-03-13	COLLEGEVILLE	NS	8201000	-62.02	45.48	76	-3	-2	-1	1
4576	2008-03-20	COLLEGEVILLE	NS	8201000	-62.02	45.48	76	-5	-4	-1	1
4577	2008-12-21	COLLEGEVILLE	NS	8201000	-62.02	45.48	76	-13	-6.5	-6.5	1
4578	2008-12-29	COLLEGEVILLE	NS	8201000	-62.02	45.48	76	-4	-3	-1	1
4579	2009-01-09	COLLEGEVILLE	NS	8201000	-62.02	45.48	76	-4	-2.5	-1.5	1
4580	2012-01-23	COLLEGEVILLE	NS	8201000	-62.02	45.48	76	-9	-8	-1	1
4581	2013-01-01	COLLEGEVILLE	NS	8201000	-62.02	45.48	76	-4	-2	-2	1
4582	2013-02-04	COLLEGEVILLE	NS	8201000	-62.02	45.48	76	-4	-1	-3	1
4583	2013-02-19	COLLEGEVILLE	NS	8201000	-62.02	45.48	76	-1	0	-1	1
4584	2013-03-09	COLLEGEVILLE	NS	8201000	-62.02	45.48	76	-1	0	-1	1
4585	2013-11-25	COLLEGEVILLE	NS	8201000	-62.02	45.48	76	-5	-3	-2	1
4586	2013-12-11	COLLEGEVILLE	NS	8201000	-62.02	45.48	76	-12	-10	-2	1
4587	2013-12-12	COLLEGEVILLE	NS	8201000	-62.02	45.48	76	-18	-12	-6	1
4588	2013-12-16	COLLEGEVILLE	NS	8201000	-62.02	45.48	76	-3.5	-2.5	-1	1
4589	2013-12-22	COLLEGEVILLE	NS	8201000	-62.02	45.48	76	-4	0	-4	1

4590	2013-12-27	COLLEGEVILLE	NS	8201000	-62.02	45.48	76	-5	-3	-2	1
4591	2014-01-26	COLLEGEVILLE	NS	8201000	-62.02	45.48	76	-2	0	-2	1
4592	2014-02-16	COLLEGEVILLE	NS	8201000	-62.02	45.48	76	-9	-5	-4	1
4593	1933-12-09	PIERSON	MAN	501A7AR	-101.27	49.18	446	-22.3	-20	-2.3	1
4594	1933-12-12	PIERSON	MAN	501A7AR	-101.27	49.18	446	-22.3	-21.1	-1.2	1
4595	1934-01-27	PIERSON	MAN	501A7AR	-101.27	49.18	446	-20.7	-1.1	-19.6	1
4596	1935-03-15	PIERSON	MAN	501A7AR	-101.27	49.18	446	-2.4	-2.2	-0.2	1
4597	1935-10-20	PIERSON	MAN	501A7AR	-101.27	49.18	446	-1.4	-1.1	-0.3	1
4598	1935-12-22	PIERSON	MAN	501A7AR	-101.27	49.18	446	-17	-12.8	-4.2	1
4599	1936-02-24	PIERSON	MAN	501A7AR	-101.27	49.18	446	-17.1	-15	-2.1	1
4600	1937-11-13	PIERSON	MAN	501A7AR	-101.27	49.18	446	-2.8	-2.2	-0.6	1
4601	1937-11-26	PIERSON	MAN	501A7AR	-101.27	49.18	446	-12.7	-2.2	-10.5	1
4602	1938-11-02	PIERSON	MAN	501A7AR	-101.27	49.18	446	0.6	1.1	-0.5	1
4603	1939-12-11	PIERSON	MAN	501A7AR	-101.27	49.18	446	-3.3	-2.2	-1.1	1
4604	1940-03-17	PIERSON	MAN	501A7AR	-101.27	49.18	446	2	2.8	-0.8	1
4605	1940-10-04	PIERSON	MAN	501A7AR	-101.27	49.18	446	13.9	14.4	-0.5	1
4606	1940-11-26	PIERSON	MAN	501A7AR	-101.27	49.18	446	-11.7	-9.4	-2.3	1
4607	1990-04-10	SACHS HARBOUR	NWT	2503648	-125.27	72	88	-17	-16	-1	1
4608	1995-03-21	SACHS HARBOUR	NWT	2503648	-125.27	72	88	-31	-26	-5	1
4609	2013-11-26	SACHS HARBOUR	NWT	2503648	-125.27	72	88	-19.2	-18.3	-0.9	1
4610	1918-12-04	STETTLER NORTH	ALTA	3016124	-112.72	52.33	795	-5.1	-4.4	-0.7	1
4611	1919-03-24	STETTLER NORTH	ALTA	3016124	-112.72	52.33	795	-9	-7.8	-1.2	1
4612	1919-10-29	STETTLER NORTH	ALTA	3016124	-112.72	52.33	795	-9	-7.8	-1.2	1
4613	1919-11-25	STETTLER NORTH	ALTA	3016124	-112.72	52.33	795	-30.4	-28.9	-1.5	1
4614	1919-11-26	STETTLER NORTH	ALTA	3016124	-112.72	52.33	795	-21.5	-21.1	-0.4	1
4615	1919-11-27	STETTLER NORTH	ALTA	3016124	-112.72	52.33	795	-25.4	-24.4	-1	1
4616	1920-01-13	STETTLER NORTH	ALTA	3016124	-112.72	52.33	795	-11.3	-10	-1.3	1
4617	1920-01-21	STETTLER NORTH	ALTA	3016124	-112.72	52.33	795	-30.4	-30	-0.4	1
4618	1920-01-29	STETTLER NORTH	ALTA	3016124	-112.72	52.33	795	-21.5	-21.1	-0.4	1
4619	1922-06-21	STETTLER NORTH	ALTA	3016124	-112.72	52.33	795	20	21.1	-1.1	1
4620	1922-12-13	STETTLER NORTH	ALTA	3016124	-112.72	52.33	795	-22.6	-22.2	-0.4	1
4621	1922-12-18	STETTLER NORTH	ALTA	3016124	-112.72	52.33	795	-16.5	-16.1	-0.4	1
4622	1922-12-19	STETTLER NORTH	ALTA	3016124	-112.72	52.33	795	-11.3	-10.6	-0.7	1
4623	1923-02-01	STETTLER NORTH	ALTA	3016124	-112.72	52.33	795	-20.9	-20.6	-0.3	1

4624	1924-01-17	STETTLER NORTH	ALTA	3016124	-112.72	52.33	795	-31.5	-30.6	-0.9	1
4625	1924-11-05	STETTLER NORTH	ALTA	3016124	-112.72	52.33	795	-9.5	-8.9	-0.6	1
4626	1924-12-05	STETTLER NORTH	ALTA	3016124	-112.72	52.33	795	-12.5	-12.2	-0.3	1
4627	1924-12-13	STETTLER NORTH	ALTA	3016124	-112.72	52.33	795	-6.5	-6.1	-0.4	1
4628	1924-12-14	STETTLER NORTH	ALTA	3016124	-112.72	52.33	795	-18.7	-17.8	-0.9	1
4629	1924-12-25	STETTLER NORTH	ALTA	3016124	-112.72	52.33	795	-11.3	-11.1	-0.2	1
4630	1924-12-30	STETTLER NORTH	ALTA	3016124	-112.72	52.33	795	-22.6	-21.7	-0.9	1
4631	1925-01-27	STETTLER NORTH	ALTA	3016124	-112.72	52.33	795	-19.3	-18.9	-0.4	1
4632	1925-01-30	STETTLER NORTH	ALTA	3016124	-112.72	52.33	795	-29.8	-28.3	-1.5	1
4633	1925-03-08	STETTLER NORTH	ALTA	3016124	-112.72	52.33	795	-14.2	-13.3	-0.9	1
4634	1925-03-11	STETTLER NORTH	ALTA	3016124	-112.72	52.33	795	-19.3	-11.1	-8.2	1
4635	1925-12-12	STETTLER NORTH	ALTA	3016124	-112.72	52.33	795	-7.1	-6.7	-0.4	1
4636	1925-12-17	STETTLER NORTH	ALTA	3016124	-112.72	52.33	795	-4.4	-3.9	-0.5	1
4637	1926-01-31	STETTLER NORTH	ALTA	3016124	-112.72	52.33	795	-14.7	-13.3	-1.4	1
4638	1926-02-16	STETTLER NORTH	ALTA	3016124	-112.72	52.33	795	-17.1	-16.1	-1	1
4639	1926-03-03	STETTLER NORTH	ALTA	3016124	-112.72	52.33	795	-5.1	-5	-0.1	1
4640	1926-03-24	STETTLER NORTH	ALTA	3016124	-112.72	52.33	795	-4.4	-3.9	-0.5	1
4641	1926-04-02	STETTLER NORTH	ALTA	3016124	-112.72	52.33	795	-10.2	-9.4	-0.8	1
4642	1926-09-10	STETTLER NORTH	ALTA	3016124	-112.72	52.33	795	6.5	6.7	-0.2	1
4643	1926-11-19	STETTLER NORTH	ALTA	3016124	-112.72	52.33	795	-17.1	-16.7	-0.4	1
4644	1926-11-29	STETTLER NORTH	ALTA	3016124	-112.72	52.33	795	-18.7	-17.8	-0.9	1
4645	1926-12-12	STETTLER NORTH	ALTA	3016124	-112.72	52.33	795	-27.1	-26.1	-1	1
4646	1927-02-14	STETTLER NORTH	ALTA	3016124	-112.72	52.33	795	-23.2	-22.2	-1	1
4647	1927-03-08	STETTLER NORTH	ALTA	3016124	-112.72	52.33	795	-6.5	-6.1	-0.4	1
4648	1927-11-12	STETTLER NORTH	ALTA	3016124	-112.72	52.33	795	-11.9	-11.7	-0.2	1
4649	1927-11-18	STETTLER NORTH	ALTA	3016124	-112.72	52.33	795	-17	-16.7	-0.3	1
4650	1927-11-19	STETTLER NORTH	ALTA	3016124	-112.72	52.33	795	-24.3	-22.8	-1.5	1
4651	1927-11-20	STETTLER NORTH	ALTA	3016124	-112.72	52.33	795	-21.5	-21.1	-0.4	1
4652	1927-11-28	STETTLER NORTH	ALTA	3016124	-112.72	52.33	795	-14.7	-14.4	-0.3	1
4653	1927-12-05	STETTLER NORTH	ALTA	3016124	-112.72	52.33	795	-9	-8.3	-0.7	1
4654	1927-12-22	STETTLER NORTH	ALTA	3016124	-112.72	52.33	795	-16.5	-15.6	-0.9	1
4655	1927-12-27	STETTLER NORTH	ALTA	3016124	-112.72	52.33	795	-24.8	-23.3	-1.5	1
4656	1928-01-13	STETTLER NORTH	ALTA	3016124	-112.72	52.33	795	-10.7	-10.6	-0.1	1
4657	1933-01-16	STETTLER NORTH	ALTA	3016124	-112.72	52.33	795	-16.5	0.6	-17.1	1

4658	1933-02-07	STETTLER NORTH	ALTA	3016124	-112.72	52.33	795	-33.7	-32.2	-1.5	1
4659	1933-12-06	STETTLER NORTH	ALTA	3016124	-112.72	52.33	795	-14.7	-14.4	-0.3	1
4660	1933-12-09	STETTLER NORTH	ALTA	3016124	-112.72	52.33	795	-16.5	-16.1	-0.4	1
4661	1933-12-17	STETTLER NORTH	ALTA	3016124	-112.72	52.33	795	-24.8	-23.3	-1.5	1
4662	1933-12-28	STETTLER NORTH	ALTA	3016124	-112.72	52.33	795	-27.6	-26.1	-1.5	1
4663	1934-01-22	STETTLER NORTH	ALTA	3016124	-112.72	52.33	795	-29.3	-8.3	-21	1
4664	1934-01-25	STETTLER NORTH	ALTA	3016124	-112.72	52.33	795	-7.7	-4.4	-3.3	1
4665	1934-02-17	STETTLER NORTH	ALTA	3016124	-112.72	52.33	795	-11.9	-7.8	-4.1	1
4666	1934-02-19	STETTLER NORTH	ALTA	3016124	-112.72	52.33	795	-12.5	-8.9	-3.6	1
4667	1934-02-20	STETTLER NORTH	ALTA	3016124	-112.72	52.33	795	-20.9	-12.2	-8.7	1
4668	1934-03-08	STETTLER NORTH	ALTA	3016124	-112.72	52.33	795	-18.2	-15.6	-2.6	1
4669	1934-03-14	STETTLER NORTH	ALTA	3016124	-112.72	52.33	795	-9	-5.6	-3.4	1
4670	1934-03-19	STETTLER NORTH	ALTA	3016124	-112.72	52.33	795	-6.5	-1.1	-5.4	1
4671	1935-01-01	STETTLER NORTH	ALTA	3016124	-112.72	52.33	795	-13.1	-12.2	-0.9	1
4672	1935-01-11	STETTLER NORTH	ALTA	3016124	-112.72	52.33	795	-13.6	-12.2	-1.4	1
4673	1935-01-15	STETTLER NORTH	ALTA	3016124	-112.72	52.33	795	-34.8	-29.4	-5.4	1
4674	1935-01-16	STETTLER NORTH	ALTA	3016124	-112.72	52.33	795	-34.8	-25.6	-9.2	1
4675	1935-10-29	STETTLER NORTH	ALTA	3016124	-112.72	52.33	795	-15.9	-15.6	-0.3	1
4676	1937-01-18	STETTLER NORTH	ALTA	3016124	-112.72	52.33	795	-24.8	-23.3	-1.5	1
4677	1937-01-23	STETTLER NORTH	ALTA	3016124	-112.72	52.33	795	-11.3	-6.7	-4.6	1
4678	1937-01-26	STETTLER NORTH	ALTA	3016124	-112.72	52.33	795	-27.1	-24.4	-2.7	1
4679	1937-02-01	STETTLER NORTH	ALTA	3016124	-112.72	52.33	795	-23.7	-23.3	-0.4	1
4680	1937-02-05	STETTLER NORTH	ALTA	3016124	-112.72	52.33	795	-30.4	-30	-0.4	1
4681	1937-02-07	STETTLER NORTH	ALTA	3016124	-112.72	52.33	795	-22.6	-22.2	-0.4	1
4682	1937-11-12	STETTLER NORTH	ALTA	3016124	-112.72	52.33	795	-7.8	-6.7	-1.1	1
4683	1937-12-06	STETTLER NORTH	ALTA	3016124	-112.72	52.33	795	-6.5	-5.6	-0.9	1
4684	1937-12-07	STETTLER NORTH	ALTA	3016124	-112.72	52.33	795	-25.9	-24.4	-1.5	1
4685	1937-12-22	STETTLER NORTH	ALTA	3016124	-112.72	52.33	795	-24.8	-17.8	-7	1
4686	1938-12-25	STETTLER NORTH	ALTA	3016124	-112.72	52.33	795	-10.2	-8.9	-1.3	1
4687	1938-12-26	STETTLER NORTH	ALTA	3016124	-112.72	52.33	795	-27.1	-20	-7.1	1
4688	1939-01-20	STETTLER NORTH	ALTA	3016124	-112.72	52.33	795	-11.3	-7.8	-3.5	1
4689	1940-12-10	STETTLER NORTH	ALTA	3016124	-112.72	52.33	795	-19.3	-6.7	-12.6	1
4690	1940-12-23	STETTLER NORTH	ALTA	3016124	-112.72	52.33	795	-6.4	-4.4	-2	1
4691	1940-12-26	STETTLER NORTH	ALTA	3016124	-112.72	52.33	795	-11.3	-7.8	-3.5	1

4692	1941-01-15	STETTLER NORTH	ALTA	3016124	-112.72	52.33	795	-13.6	-12.2	-1.4	1
4693	1941-01-23	STETTLER NORTH	ALTA	3016124	-112.72	52.33	795	-24.8	-23.3	-1.5	1
4694	1941-03-15	STETTLER NORTH	ALTA	3016124	-112.72	52.33	795	-14.7	-14.4	-0.3	1
4695	1941-12-08	STETTLER NORTH	ALTA	3016124	-112.72	52.33	795	-5.1	-4.4	-0.7	1
4696	1942-11-16	STETTLER NORTH	ALTA	3016124	-112.72	52.33	795	-10.2	-10	-0.2	1
4697	1942-12-06	STETTLER NORTH	ALTA	3016124	-112.72	52.33	795	-15.9	-14.4	-1.5	1
4698	1943-02-21	STETTLER NORTH	ALTA	3016124	-112.72	52.33	795	-6.5	-3.3	-3.2	1
4699	1943-02-26	STETTLER NORTH	ALTA	3016124	-112.72	52.33	795	-7.8	-4.4	-3.4	1
4700	1943-03-12	STETTLER NORTH	ALTA	3016124	-112.72	52.33	795	-14.7	-11.1	-3.6	1
4701	1943-03-13	STETTLER NORTH	ALTA	3016124	-112.72	52.33	795	-17.1	-15.6	-1.5	1
4702	1943-03-24	STETTLER NORTH	ALTA	3016124	-112.72	52.33	795	-0.7	0	-0.7	1
4703	1944-01-02	STETTLER NORTH	ALTA	3016124	-112.72	52.33	795	-15.9	-15.6	-0.3	1
4704	1944-03-22	STETTLER NORTH	ALTA	3016124	-112.72	52.33	795	-10.1	-3.3	-6.8	1
4705	1944-11-23	STETTLER NORTH	ALTA	3016124	-112.72	52.33	795	-6.5	-3.3	-3.2	1
4706	1922-03-22	THETFORD MINES	QUE	7028441	-71.35	46.1	381	-1.2	-0.6	-0.6	1
4707	1922-03-31	THETFORD MINES	QUE	7028441	-71.35	46.1	381	-3.8	-1.3	-2.5	1
4708	1922-04-11	THETFORD MINES	QUE	7028441	-71.35	46.1	381	4.3	6.8	-2.5	1
4709	1922-04-13	THETFORD MINES	QUE	7028441	-71.35	46.1	381	3.2	4.2	-1	1
4710	1922-05-05	THETFORD MINES	QUE	7028441	-71.35	46.1	381	4.9	6.9	-2	1
4711	1922-05-08	THETFORD MINES	QUE	7028441	-71.35	46.1	381	7.1	7.6	-0.5	1
4712	1922-06-18	THETFORD MINES	QUE	7028441	-71.35	46.1	381	10.1	11.1	-1	1
4713	1922-10-29	THETFORD MINES	QUE	7028441	-71.35	46.1	381	-1.2	0	-1.2	1
4714	1922-11-07	THETFORD MINES	QUE	7028441	-71.35	46.1	381	-1.8	0	-1.8	1
4715	1922-11-19	THETFORD MINES	QUE	7028441	-71.35	46.1	381	-0.1	1.9	-2	1
4716	1922-11-20	THETFORD MINES	QUE	7028441	-71.35	46.1	381	-0.6	0.8	-1.4	1
4717	1922-11-21	THETFORD MINES	QUE	7028441	-71.35	46.1	381	-1.2	0.8	-2	1
4718	1922-11-22	THETFORD MINES	QUE	7028441	-71.35	46.1	381	-5.7	-5.5	-0.2	1
4719	1922-11-24	THETFORD MINES	QUE	7028441	-71.35	46.1	381	-3.3	-0.6	-2.7	1
4720	1923-03-24	THETFORD MINES	QUE	7028441	-71.35	46.1	381	-0.1	0.8	-0.9	1
4721	1923-04-05	THETFORD MINES	QUE	7028441	-71.35	46.1	381	0.7	0.8	-0.1	1
4722	1923-07-25	THETFORD MINES	QUE	7028441	-71.35	46.1	381	13	13.4	-0.4	1
4723	1923-07-28	THETFORD MINES	QUE	7028441	-71.35	46.1	381	10.1	10.6	-0.5	1
4724	1923-10-03	THETFORD MINES	QUE	7028441	-71.35	46.1	381	7.6	9.1	-1.5	1
4725	1923-10-04	THETFORD MINES	QUE	7028441	-71.35	46.1	381	8.3	8.6	-0.3	1

4726	1923-10-07	THETFORD MINES	QUE	7028441	-71.35	46.1	381	3.2	5.3	-2.1	1
4727	1923-10-25	THETFORD MINES	QUE	7028441	-71.35	46.1	381	8.3	9	-0.7	1
4728	1923-11-07	THETFORD MINES	QUE	7028441	-71.35	46.1	381	5.4	8.6	-3.2	1
4729	1923-11-08	THETFORD MINES	QUE	7028441	-71.35	46.1	381	-2.3	0.3	-2.6	1
4730	1923-11-13	THETFORD MINES	QUE	7028441	-71.35	46.1	381	-1.2	0.3	-1.5	1
4731	1923-11-23	THETFORD MINES	QUE	7028441	-71.35	46.1	381	-1.2	0	-1.2	1
4732	1923-11-24	THETFORD MINES	QUE	7028441	-71.35	46.1	381	0.7	1.8	-1.1	1
4733	1923-11-25	THETFORD MINES	QUE	7028441	-71.35	46.1	381	2	2.7	-0.7	1
4734	1923-11-27	THETFORD MINES	QUE	7028441	-71.35	46.1	381	3.2	4.1	-0.9	1
4735	1923-11-28	THETFORD MINES	QUE	7028441	-71.35	46.1	381	-1.8	0	-1.8	1
4736	1923-12-01	THETFORD MINES	QUE	7028441	-71.35	46.1	381	0.6	2.7	-2.1	1
4737	1923-12-02	THETFORD MINES	QUE	7028441	-71.35	46.1	381	0	1.1	-1.1	1
4738	1923-12-03	THETFORD MINES	QUE	7028441	-71.35	46.1	381	0.7	1.1	-0.4	1
4739	1923-12-04	THETFORD MINES	QUE	7028441	-71.35	46.1	381	0.7	1.1	-0.4	1
4740	1923-12-09	THETFORD MINES	QUE	7028441	-71.35	46.1	381	4.3	6	-1.7	1
4741	1923-12-21	THETFORD MINES	QUE	7028441	-71.35	46.1	381	3.2	4.1	-0.9	1
4742	1923-12-22	THETFORD MINES	QUE	7028441	-71.35	46.1	381	0.7	3.3	-2.6	1
4743	1923-12-23	THETFORD MINES	QUE	7028441	-71.35	46.1	381	-2.3	0.3	-2.6	1
4744	1924-03-05	THETFORD MINES	QUE	7028441	-71.35	46.1	381	-0.6	0	-0.6	1
4745	1924-03-06	THETFORD MINES	QUE	7028441	-71.35	46.1	381	0	1.1	-1.1	1
4746	1924-03-07	THETFORD MINES	QUE	7028441	-71.35	46.1	381	0.6	1.1	-0.5	1
4747	1924-03-10	THETFORD MINES	QUE	7028441	-71.35	46.1	381	-0.1	0.3	-0.4	1
4748	1924-04-07	THETFORD MINES	QUE	7028441	-71.35	46.1	381	0.8	1.8	-1	1
4749	1924-04-08	THETFORD MINES	QUE	7028441	-71.35	46.1	381	2	2.5	-0.5	1
4750	1924-04-11	THETFORD MINES	QUE	7028441	-71.35	46.1	381	-1.8	0	-1.8	1
4751	1924-04-19	THETFORD MINES	QUE	7028441	-71.35	46.1	381	0.7	1.8	-1.1	1
4752	1924-04-22	THETFORD MINES	QUE	7028441	-71.35	46.1	381	-0.1	1.8	-1.9	1
4753	1924-05-01	THETFORD MINES	QUE	7028441	-71.35	46.1	381	2	3.3	-1.3	1
4754	1924-05-04	THETFORD MINES	QUE	7028441	-71.35	46.1	381	2.5	4.3	-1.8	1
4755	1924-10-07	THETFORD MINES	QUE	7028441	-71.35	46.1	381	10.1	11.1	-1	1
4756	1924-10-08	THETFORD MINES	QUE	7028441	-71.35	46.1	381	7.1	7.6	-0.5	1
4757	1925-03-22	THETFORD MINES	QUE	7028441	-71.35	46.1	381	-2.3	-1.5	-0.8	1
4758	1925-12-04	THETFORD MINES	QUE	7028441	-71.35	46.1	381	5.9	6.2	-0.3	1
4759	1925-12-07	THETFORD MINES	QUE	7028441	-71.35	46.1	381	0	0.8	-0.8	1

4760	1925-12-08	THETFORD MINES	QUE	7028441	-71.35	46.1	381	-1.2	0	-1.2	1
4761	1926-01-05	THETFORD MINES	QUE	7028441	-71.35	46.1	381	-1.8	0.4	-2.2	1
4762	1926-01-06	THETFORD MINES	QUE	7028441	-71.35	46.1	381	2.5	4.2	-1.7	1
4763	1926-01-17	THETFORD MINES	QUE	7028441	-71.35	46.1	381	-1.2	0	-1.2	1
4764	1926-01-19	THETFORD MINES	QUE	7028441	-71.35	46.1	381	-0.6	0.4	-1	1
4765	1926-03-24	THETFORD MINES	QUE	7028441	-71.35	46.1	381	1.3	1.8	-0.5	1
4766	1926-04-25	THETFORD MINES	QUE	7028441	-71.35	46.1	381	6.4	7.7	-1.3	1
4767	1926-05-04	THETFORD MINES	QUE	7028441	-71.35	46.1	381	0.7	1.1	-0.4	1
4768	1926-05-20	THETFORD MINES	QUE	7028441	-71.35	46.1	381	8.9	9.2	-0.3	1
4769	1926-05-24	THETFORD MINES	QUE	7028441	-71.35	46.1	381	4.9	5.3	-0.4	1
4770	1926-06-10	THETFORD MINES	QUE	7028441	-71.35	46.1	381	11.9	12	-0.1	1
4771	1926-09-25	THETFORD MINES	QUE	7028441	-71.35	46.1	381	14.4	14.9	-0.5	1
4772	1926-09-30	THETFORD MINES	QUE	7028441	-71.35	46.1	381	10.6	11.6	-1	1
4773	1926-10-15	THETFORD MINES	QUE	7028441	-71.35	46.1	381	3.7	4.3	-0.6	1
4774	1926-10-21	THETFORD MINES	QUE	7028441	-71.35	46.1	381	0.7	4.2	-3.5	1
4775	1926-10-30	THETFORD MINES	QUE	7028441	-71.35	46.1	381	4.9	5.2	-0.3	1
4776	1926-11-10	THETFORD MINES	QUE	7028441	-71.35	46.1	381	5.9	9.3	-3.4	1
4777	1926-11-17	THETFORD MINES	QUE	7028441	-71.35	46.1	381	3.7	8.2	-4.5	1
4778	1926-11-20	THETFORD MINES	QUE	7028441	-71.35	46.1	381	-1.8	0.4	-2.2	1
4779	1927-01-30	THETFORD MINES	QUE	7028441	-71.35	46.1	381	3.7	4.3	-0.6	1
4780	1927-02-08	THETFORD MINES	QUE	7028441	-71.35	46.1	381	-6.5	-6.1	-0.4	1
4781	1927-02-18	THETFORD MINES	QUE	7028441	-71.35	46.1	381	-1.2	-0.6	-0.6	1
4782	1927-03-08	THETFORD MINES	QUE	7028441	-71.35	46.1	381	0	1.8	-1.8	1
4783	1927-03-14	THETFORD MINES	QUE	7028441	-71.35	46.1	381	6.4	6.9	-0.5	1
4784	1927-05-05	THETFORD MINES	QUE	7028441	-71.35	46.1	381	7.7	8.2	-0.5	1
4785	1927-05-07	THETFORD MINES	QUE	7028441	-71.35	46.1	381	7.1	8.5	-1.4	1
4786	1927-05-13	THETFORD MINES	QUE	7028441	-71.35	46.1	381	8.9	9	-0.1	1
4787	1927-05-15	THETFORD MINES	QUE	7028441	-71.35	46.1	381	7.6	9.1	-1.5	1
4788	1927-05-18	THETFORD MINES	QUE	7028441	-71.35	46.1	381	8.8	9.2	-0.4	1
4789	1927-05-27	THETFORD MINES	QUE	7028441	-71.35	46.1	381	6.5	7.6	-1.1	1
4790	1927-06-24	THETFORD MINES	QUE	7028441	-71.35	46.1	381	14.4	15.5	-1.1	1
4791	1927-09-22	THETFORD MINES	QUE	7028441	-71.35	46.1	381	7.1	9	-1.9	1
4792	1927-10-19	THETFORD MINES	QUE	7028441	-71.35	46.1	381	10.1	12	-1.9	1
4793	1927-10-20	THETFORD MINES	QUE	7028441	-71.35	46.1	381	8.9	10.6	-1.7	1

4794	1927-10-21	THETFORD MINES	QUE	7028441	-71.35	46.1	381	8.3	10	-1.7	1
4795	1928-01-10	THETFORD MINES	QUE	7028441	-71.35	46.1	381	-0.6	-0.1	-0.5	1
4796	1928-05-06	THETFORD MINES	QUE	7028441	-71.35	46.1	381	6.5	8.6	-2.1	1
4797	1928-11-10	THETFORD MINES	QUE	7028441	-71.35	46.1	381	-6.5	-5.4	-1.1	1
4798	1929-01-19	THETFORD MINES	QUE	7028441	-71.35	46.1	381	0.6	0.8	-0.2	1
4799	1929-03-16	THETFORD MINES	QUE	7028441	-71.35	46.1	381	2.6	3.2	-0.6	1
4800	1929-04-16	THETFORD MINES	QUE	7028441	-71.35	46.1	381	-0.6	0.4	-1	1
4801	1929-04-29	THETFORD MINES	QUE	7028441	-71.35	46.1	381	4.3	6.9	-2.6	1
4802	1929-08-04	THETFORD MINES	QUE	7028441	-71.35	46.1	381	11.1	12.2	-1.1	1
4803	1929-10-17	THETFORD MINES	QUE	7028441	-71.35	46.1	381	0.8	1.1	-0.3	1
4804	1929-11-15	THETFORD MINES	QUE	7028441	-71.35	46.1	381	4.9	5.2	-0.3	1
4805	1929-11-18	THETFORD MINES	QUE	7028441	-71.35	46.1	381	-1.2	0.3	-1.5	1
4806	1930-04-19	THETFORD MINES	QUE	7028441	-71.35	46.1	381	6.4	8.2	-1.8	1
4807	1930-11-14	THETFORD MINES	QUE	7028441	-71.35	46.1	381	8.8	9.2	-0.4	1
4808	1930-11-18	THETFORD MINES	QUE	7028441	-71.35	46.1	381	5.3	7.7	-2.4	1
4809	1931-09-07	THETFORD MINES	QUE	7028441	-71.35	46.1	381	15.6	17.1	-1.5	1
4810	1931-09-26	THETFORD MINES	QUE	7028441	-71.35	46.1	381	8.3	9.2	-0.9	1
4811	1931-10-08	THETFORD MINES	QUE	7028441	-71.35	46.1	381	11.5	11.6	-0.1	1
4812	1931-10-28	THETFORD MINES	QUE	7028441	-71.35	46.1	381	6.5	8.2	-1.7	1
4813	1931-10-29	THETFORD MINES	QUE	7028441	-71.35	46.1	381	7.1	7.6	-0.5	1
4814	1931-10-31	THETFORD MINES	QUE	7028441	-71.35	46.1	381	5.3	6.1	-0.8	1
4815	1931-11-25	THETFORD MINES	QUE	7028441	-71.35	46.1	381	4.3	6.9	-2.6	1
4816	1931-12-01	THETFORD MINES	QUE	7028441	-71.35	46.1	381	-3.8	-2.3	-1.5	1
4817	1932-04-03	THETFORD MINES	QUE	7028441	-71.35	46.1	381	-2.8	-2.1	-0.7	1
4818	1932-05-20	THETFORD MINES	QUE	7028441	-71.35	46.1	381	12.3	13	-0.7	1
4819	1932-10-07	THETFORD MINES	QUE	7028441	-71.35	46.1	381	9.5	9.6	-0.1	1
4820	1932-10-27	THETFORD MINES	QUE	7028441	-71.35	46.1	381	10.1	10.6	-0.5	1
4821	1932-11-12	THETFORD MINES	QUE	7028441	-71.35	46.1	381	1.3	1.8	-0.5	1
4822	1932-11-17	THETFORD MINES	QUE	7028441	-71.35	46.1	381	-5.7	-4.8	-0.9	1
4823	1932-12-22	THETFORD MINES	QUE	7028441	-71.35	46.1	381	-1.2	0.3	-1.5	1
4824	1932-12-26	THETFORD MINES	QUE	7028441	-71.35	46.1	381	5.9	6.9	-1	1
4825	1932-12-31	THETFORD MINES	QUE	7028441	-71.35	46.1	381	-1.8	0.3	-2.1	1
4826	1933-03-03	THETFORD MINES	QUE	7028441	-71.35	46.1	381	-1.8	-1.4	-0.4	1
4827	1933-04-04	THETFORD MINES	QUE	7028441	-71.35	46.1	381	-0.1	0.3	-0.4	1

4828	1933-04-18	THETFORD MINES	QUE	7028441	-71.35	46.1	381	5.3	6.1	-0.8	1
4829	1933-04-26	THETFORD MINES	QUE	7028441	-71.35	46.1	381	-1.2	0.7	-1.9	1
4830	1933-05-27	THETFORD MINES	QUE	7028441	-71.35	46.1	381	6.5	10	-3.5	1
4831	1933-09-19	THETFORD MINES	QUE	7028441	-71.35	46.1	381	11.1	12.3	-1.2	1
4832	1933-10-07	THETFORD MINES	QUE	7028441	-71.35	46.1	381	7.1	8.9	-1.8	1
4833	1933-10-08	THETFORD MINES	QUE	7028441	-71.35	46.1	381	8.8	9.2	-0.4	1
4834	1933-10-25	THETFORD MINES	QUE	7028441	-71.35	46.1	381	-1.8	-0.6	-1.2	1
4835	1933-11-14	THETFORD MINES	QUE	7028441	-71.35	46.1	381	-4.3	-3.3	-1	1
4836	1933-12-06	THETFORD MINES	QUE	7028441	-71.35	46.1	381	-1.8	-1.4	-0.4	1
4837	1934-01-08	THETFORD MINES	QUE	7028441	-71.35	46.1	381	0	0.8	-0.8	1
4838	1934-01-12	THETFORD MINES	QUE	7028441	-71.35	46.1	381	-1.8	-0.6	-1.2	1
4839	1934-03-06	THETFORD MINES	QUE	7028441	-71.35	46.1	381	-1.2	0.8	-2	1
4840	1934-03-18	THETFORD MINES	QUE	7028441	-71.35	46.1	381	-3.8	-2.3	-1.5	1
4841	1934-05-07	THETFORD MINES	QUE	7028441	-71.35	46.1	381	4.3	4.4	-0.1	1
4842	1934-11-05	THETFORD MINES	QUE	7028441	-71.35	46.1	381	8.3	10	-1.7	1
4843	1934-11-24	THETFORD MINES	QUE	7028441	-71.35	46.1	381	-1.2	0.3	-1.5	1
4844	1934-12-02	THETFORD MINES	QUE	7028441	-71.35	46.1	381	0	1.1	-1.1	1
4845	1935-04-30	THETFORD MINES	QUE	7028441	-71.35	46.1	381	5.9	8.6	-2.7	1
4846	1935-05-01	THETFORD MINES	QUE	7028441	-71.35	46.1	381	-2.8	-2.4	-0.4	1
4847	1935-09-27	THETFORD MINES	QUE	7028441	-71.35	46.1	381	8.9	10	-1.1	1
4848	1935-10-23	THETFORD MINES	QUE	7028441	-71.35	46.1	381	9.5	10	-0.5	1
4849	1935-11-06	THETFORD MINES	QUE	7028441	-71.35	46.1	381	5.3	6.1	-0.8	1
4850	1935-11-12	THETFORD MINES	QUE	7028441	-71.35	46.1	381	0	0.6	-0.6	1
4851	1935-11-13	THETFORD MINES	QUE	7028441	-71.35	46.1	381	-0.6	0	-0.6	1
4852	1935-11-23	THETFORD MINES	QUE	7028441	-71.35	46.1	381	-6.2	-6.1	-0.1	1
4853	1935-12-11	THETFORD MINES	QUE	7028441	-71.35	46.1	381	-1.2	0	-1.2	1
4854	1935-12-12	THETFORD MINES	QUE	7028441	-71.35	46.1	381	-4.8	-3.2	-1.6	1
4855	1936-01-04	THETFORD MINES	QUE	7028441	-71.35	46.1	381	-2.3	-2.2	-0.1	1
4856	1936-05-19	THETFORD MINES	QUE	7028441	-71.35	46.1	381	11.4	12.3	-0.9	1
4857	1936-09-30	THETFORD MINES	QUE	7028441	-71.35	46.1	381	11.1	11.7	-0.6	1
4858	1936-10-18	THETFORD MINES	QUE	7028441	-71.35	46.1	381	2.5	3.2	-0.7	1
4859	1936-11-04	THETFORD MINES	QUE	7028441	-71.35	46.1	381	3.7	4.5	-0.8	1
4860	1936-12-28	THETFORD MINES	QUE	7028441	-71.35	46.1	381	-1.8	-0.6	-1.2	1
4861	1937-01-01	THETFORD MINES	QUE	7028441	-71.35	46.1	381	-0.6	0.4	-1	1

4862	1937-05-14	THETFORD MINES	QUE	7028441	-71.35	46.1	381	3.7	4.4	-0.7	1
4863	1937-05-20	THETFORD MINES	QUE	7028441	-71.35	46.1	381	7.6	8.2	-0.6	1
4864	1937-09-12	THETFORD MINES	QUE	7028441	-71.35	46.1	381	13.1	13.9	-0.8	1
4865	1937-09-20	THETFORD MINES	QUE	7028441	-71.35	46.1	381	7.6	9	-1.4	1
4866	1937-10-07	THETFORD MINES	QUE	7028441	-71.35	46.1	381	10.6	12	-1.4	1
4867	1937-10-24	THETFORD MINES	QUE	7028441	-71.35	46.1	381	5.9	6.1	-0.2	1
4868	1937-10-28	THETFORD MINES	QUE	7028441	-71.35	46.1	381	9.5	10	-0.5	1
4869	1937-10-29	THETFORD MINES	QUE	7028441	-71.35	46.1	381	7.1	8.2	-1.1	1
4870	1937-10-30	THETFORD MINES	QUE	7028441	-71.35	46.1	381	6.4	7.6	-1.2	1
4871	1937-11-03	THETFORD MINES	QUE	7028441	-71.35	46.1	381	-0.6	0.7	-1.3	1
4872	1937-11-06	THETFORD MINES	QUE	7028441	-71.35	46.1	381	0.7	1.1	-0.4	1
4873	1937-11-10	THETFORD MINES	QUE	7028441	-71.35	46.1	381	-0.6	0.2	-0.8	1
4874	1937-11-14	THETFORD MINES	QUE	7028441	-71.35	46.1	381	3.7	4.3	-0.6	1
4875	1937-11-15	THETFORD MINES	QUE	7028441	-71.35	46.1	381	3.2	3.4	-0.2	1
4876	1937-11-17	THETFORD MINES	QUE	7028441	-71.35	46.1	381	2.6	3.4	-0.8	1
4877	1937-11-18	THETFORD MINES	QUE	7028441	-71.35	46.1	381	0	0.3	-0.3	1
4878	1937-11-29	THETFORD MINES	QUE	7028441	-71.35	46.1	381	0	1.8	-1.8	1
4879	1937-12-01	THETFORD MINES	QUE	7028441	-71.35	46.1	381	-3.3	-3	-0.3	1
4880	1937-12-18	THETFORD MINES	QUE	7028441	-71.35	46.1	381	-2.8	-2.3	-0.5	1
4881	1938-02-07	THETFORD MINES	QUE	7028441	-71.35	46.1	381	-6.2	-6.1	-0.1	1
4882	1938-03-24	THETFORD MINES	QUE	7028441	-71.35	46.1	381	2.6	3.3	-0.7	1
4883	1938-03-27	THETFORD MINES	QUE	7028441	-71.35	46.1	381	-1.2	0.7	-1.9	1
4884	1938-04-01	THETFORD MINES	QUE	7028441	-71.35	46.1	381	4.3	6.2	-1.9	1
4885	1938-04-29	THETFORD MINES	QUE	7028441	-71.35	46.1	381	6.4	8.1	-1.7	1
4886	1940-10-15	THETFORD MINES	QUE	7028441	-71.35	46.1	381	4.7	4.8	-0.1	1
4887	1950-05-13	THETFORD MINES	QUE	7028441	-71.35	46.1	381	4.7	4.8	-0.1	1
4888	1950-10-13	THETFORD MINES	QUE	7028441	-71.35	46.1	381	7.8	8.8	-1	1
4889	1951-02-08	THETFORD MINES	QUE	7028441	-71.35	46.1	381	-19.8	-19.6	-0.2	1
4890	1952-10-03	THETFORD MINES	QUE	7028441	-71.35	46.1	381	7.2	7.8	-0.6	1
4891	1958-10-24	THETFORD MINES	QUE	7028441	-71.35	46.1	381	7.2	7.8	-0.6	1
4892	1959-01-05	THETFORD MINES	QUE	7028441	-71.35	46.1	381	-22.5	-22	-0.5	1
4893	1961-04-16	THETFORD MINES	QUE	7028441	-71.35	46.1	381	2.2	4.9	-2.7	1
4894	1962-12-19	THETFORD MINES	QUE	7028441	-71.35	46.1	381	-16.4	-9.1	-7.3	1
4895	1962-12-23	THETFORD MINES	QUE	7028441	-71.35	46.1	381	-11.1	-10.1	-1	1

4896	1963-01-20	THETFORD MINES	QUE	7028441	-71.35	46.1	381	-12.1	-9.1	-3	1
4897	1963-01-23	THETFORD MINES	QUE	7028441	-71.35	46.1	381	-17.5	-14.7	-2.8	1
4898	1963-01-30	THETFORD MINES	QUE	7028441	-71.35	46.1	381	-19.2	-14.3	-4.9	1
4899	1963-02-13	THETFORD MINES	QUE	7028441	-71.35	46.1	381	-14.3	-10.1	-4.2	1
4900	1963-02-14	THETFORD MINES	QUE	7028441	-71.35	46.1	381	-13.2	-12.7	-0.5	1
4901	1963-02-19	THETFORD MINES	QUE	7028441	-71.35	46.1	381	-13.2	-10.2	-3	1
4902	1963-02-20	THETFORD MINES	QUE	7028441	-71.35	46.1	381	-16.4	-12.7	-3.7	1
4903	1963-03-14	THETFORD MINES	QUE	7028441	-71.35	46.1	381	-7.4	-5.1	-2.3	1
4904	1963-03-27	THETFORD MINES	QUE	7028441	-71.35	46.1	381	0.4	1.1	-0.7	1
4905	1963-03-30	THETFORD MINES	QUE	7028441	-71.35	46.1	381	1.5	2.9	-1.4	1
4906	1963-08-22	THETFORD MINES	QUE	7028441	-71.35	46.1	381	11.3	13.7	-2.4	1
4907	1965-01-07	THETFORD MINES	QUE	7028441	-71.35	46.1	381	-11.5	-2.6	-8.9	1
4908	1965-01-15	THETFORD MINES	QUE	7028441	-71.35	46.1	381	-27	-23	-4	1
4909	1961-10-12	WAWA	ONT	6059407	-84.78	47.97	288	3.6	5	-1.4	1
4910	1961-10-18	WAWA	ONT	6059407	-84.78	47.97	288	0.7	2.4	-1.7	1
4911	1964-11-17	WAWA	ONT	6059407	-84.78	47.97	288	-4.4	-3.5	-0.9	1
4912	1964-11-25	WAWA	ONT	6059407	-84.78	47.97	288	-11.1	-5.9	-5.2	1
4913	1964-11-28	WAWA	ONT	6059407	-84.78	47.97	288	-19.2	-16.2	-3	1
4914	2015-04-20	WAWA	ONT	6059407	-84.78	47.97	288	1.1	2.6	-1.5	1
4915	2015-04-21	WAWA	ONT	6059407	-84.78	47.97	288	-0.8	-0.3	-0.5	1
4916	1913-02-08	BROME	QUE	7020840	-72.57	45.18	206	-16.8	-10.2	-6.6	1
4917	1913-02-23	BROME	QUE	7020840	-72.57	45.18	206	-11.9	-6.1	-5.8	1
4918	1916-02-18	BROME	QUE	7020840	-72.57	45.18	206	-15.1	-2.5	-12.6	1
4919	1916-02-26	BROME	QUE	7020840	-72.57	45.18	206	-8.7	2.1	-10.8	1
4920	1916-02-27	BROME	QUE	7020840	-72.57	45.18	206	-14.6	-14.1	-0.5	1
4921	1938-11-22	BROME	QUE	7020840	-72.57	45.18	206	-4.5	-3.1	-1.4	1
4922	1938-11-23	BROME	QUE	7020840	-72.57	45.18	206	-8.8	-6.5	-2.3	1
4923	1961-03-29	BROME	QUE	7020840	-72.57	45.18	206	1.2	1.5	-0.3	1
4924	1962-02-08	BROME	QUE	7020840	-72.57	45.18	206	-17.9	-12.4	-5.5	1
4925	1909-12-09	CRANBROOK	BC	1152105	-115.78	49.62	940	-11.7	-11.1	-0.6	1
4926	1909-12-11	CRANBROOK	BC	1152105	-115.78	49.62	940	-0.9	0.6	-1.5	1
4927	1910-01-28	CRANBROOK	BC	1152105	-115.78	49.62	940	-1.5	-1	-0.5	1
4928	1910-01-31	CRANBROOK	BC	1152105	-115.78	49.62	940	-0.2	0	-0.2	1
4929	1910-11-03	CRANBROOK	BC	1152105	-115.78	49.62	940	6.3	7.1	-0.8	1

4930	1911-05-25	CRANBROOK	BC	1152105	-115.78	49.62	940	1.1	1.2	-0.1	1
4931	1914-10-04	CRANBROOK	BC	1152105	-115.78	49.62	940	6.9	7.1	-0.2	1
4932	1916-02-06	CRANBROOK	BC	1152105	-115.78	49.62	940	-11.7	-11.6	-0.1	1
4933	1917-01-02	CRANBROOK	BC	1152105	-115.78	49.62	940	0.4	0.6	-0.2	1
4934	1917-11-11	CRANBROOK	BC	1152105	-115.78	49.62	940	-0.8	-0.4	-0.4	1
4935	1917-11-17	CRANBROOK	BC	1152105	-115.78	49.62	940	-1.5	-1	-0.5	1
4936	1918-02-10	CRANBROOK	BC	1152105	-115.78	49.62	940	2.2	2.7	-0.5	1
4937	1921-12-18	CRANBROOK	BC	1152105	-115.78	49.62	940	-16.7	-16.2	-0.5	1
4938	1922-04-18	CRANBROOK	BC	1152105	-115.78	49.62	940	-0.2	0.6	-0.8	1
4939	1923-05-30	CRANBROOK	BC	1152105	-115.78	49.62	940	6.3	6.5	-0.2	1
4940	1923-11-17	CRANBROOK	BC	1152105	-115.78	49.62	940	0.4	0.6	-0.2	1
4941	1928-03-08	CRANBROOK	BC	1152105	-115.78	49.62	940	5.7	6.5	-0.8	1
4942	1928-11-24	CRANBROOK	BC	1152105	-115.78	49.62	940	-0.9	-0.4	-0.5	1
4943	1928-11-29	CRANBROOK	BC	1152105	-115.78	49.62	940	-2.1	-1	-1.1	1
4944	1930-02-02	CRANBROOK	BC	1152105	-115.78	49.62	940	3.8	4.2	-0.4	1
4945	1932-12-28	CRANBROOK	BC	1152105	-115.78	49.62	940	-8.5	-7.1	-1.4	1
4946	1933-10-23	CRANBROOK	BC	1152105	-115.78	49.62	940	1.6	2	-0.4	1
4947	1933-10-31	CRANBROOK	BC	1152105	-115.78	49.62	940	-1.5	-0.4	-1.1	1
4948	1933-12-03	CRANBROOK	BC	1152105	-115.78	49.62	940	2.7	2.8	-0.1	1
4949	1933-12-16	CRANBROOK	BC	1152105	-115.78	49.62	940	-6.9	-6.6	-0.3	1
4950	1934-12-08	CRANBROOK	BC	1152105	-115.78	49.62	940	-6.9	-6.6	-0.3	1
4951	1934-12-30	CRANBROOK	BC	1152105	-115.78	49.62	940	-3.8	-3.5	-0.3	1
4952	1934-12-31	CRANBROOK	BC	1152105	-115.78	49.62	940	-3.8	-3.5	-0.3	1
4953	1935-10-20	CRANBROOK	BC	1152105	-115.78	49.62	940	5	5.4	-0.4	1
4954	1935-12-18	CRANBROOK	BC	1152105	-115.78	49.62	940	-4.9	-4.6	-0.3	1
4955	1935-12-20	CRANBROOK	BC	1152105	-115.78	49.62	940	-7.4	-7.2	-0.2	1
4956	1935-12-25	CRANBROOK	BC	1152105	-115.78	49.62	940	-5.9	-5.1	-0.8	1
4957	1938-11-19	CRANBROOK	BC	1152105	-115.78	49.62	940	4.4	4.8	-0.4	1
4958	1939-10-02	CRANBROOK	BC	1152105	-115.78	49.62	940	6.9	7.6	-0.7	1
4959	1943-04-09	CRANBROOK	BC	1152105	-115.78	49.62	940	5.7	5.9	-0.2	1
4960	1943-12-14	CRANBROOK	BC	1152105	-115.78	49.62	940	-8.5	-8.2	-0.3	1
4961	1947-11-28	CRANBROOK	BC	1152105	-115.78	49.62	940	-4.3	-4	-0.3	1
4962	1947-11-29	CRANBROOK	BC	1152105	-115.78	49.62	940	-6.4	-6.1	-0.3	1
4963	1950-01-24	CRANBROOK	BC	1152105	-115.78	49.62	940	-9.6	-9.3	-0.3	1

4964	1950-01-30	CRANBROOK	BC	1152105	-115.78	49.62	940	-30	-29.5	-0.5	1
4965	1951-01-26	CRANBROOK	BC	1152105	-115.78	49.62	940	-0.1	0.6	-0.7	1
4966	1951-11-08	CRANBROOK	BC	1152105	-115.78	49.62	940	2.2	2.7	-0.5	1
4967	1954-01-15	CRANBROOK	BC	1152105	-115.78	49.62	940	-22.3	-21.8	-0.5	1
4968	1955-01-02	CRANBROOK	BC	1152105	-115.78	49.62	940	-4.8	-4	-0.8	1
4969	1955-10-31	CRANBROOK	BC	1152105	-115.78	49.62	940	-1.5	-1	-0.5	1
4970	1955-11-10	CRANBROOK	BC	1152105	-115.78	49.62	940	-11.7	-10.5	-1.2	1
4971	1956-11-25	CRANBROOK	BC	1152105	-115.78	49.62	940	-6.4	-6.1	-0.3	1
4972	1956-12-04	CRANBROOK	BC	1152105	-115.78	49.62	940	-11.7	-11.1	-0.6	1
4973	1957-10-03	CRANBROOK	BC	1152105	-115.78	49.62	940	4.4	5.9	-1.5	1
4974	1958-01-17	CRANBROOK	BC	1152105	-115.78	49.62	940	1.1	1.2	-0.1	1
4975	1958-02-13	CRANBROOK	BC	1152105	-115.78	49.62	940	-5.9	-5.1	-0.8	1
4976	1958-11-14	CRANBROOK	BC	1152105	-115.78	49.62	940	-4.3	-4	-0.3	1
4977	1958-12-07	CRANBROOK	BC	1152105	-115.78	49.62	940	-15	-14.5	-0.5	1
4978	1959-05-25	CRANBROOK	BC	1152105	-115.78	49.62	940	6.4	7.1	-0.7	1
4979	1960-09-20	CRANBROOK	BC	1152105	-115.78	49.62	940	7	7.6	-0.6	1
4980	1962-12-12	CRANBROOK	BC	1152105	-115.78	49.62	940	-2.1	-1	-1.1	1
4981	1963-01-01	CRANBROOK	BC	1152105	-115.78	49.62	940	4.4	5.4	-1	1
4982	1964-03-22	CRANBROOK	BC	1152105	-115.78	49.62	940	-5.9	-5.6	-0.3	1
4983	1964-12-06	CRANBROOK	BC	1152105	-115.78	49.62	940	-2.1	-1	-1.1	1
4984	1965-01-19	CRANBROOK	BC	1152105	-115.78	49.62	940	-2.1	-1.6	-0.5	1
4985	1965-12-29	CRANBROOK	BC	1152105	-115.78	49.62	940	-0.9	-0.4	-0.5	1
4986	1906-03-26	MOOSONEE	ONT	6075425	-80.65	51.27	10	-5.1	-0.9	-4.2	1
4987	1918-01-10	MOOSONEE	ONT	6075425	-80.65	51.27	10	-17.4	-16.8	-0.6	1
4988	1919-12-25	MOOSONEE	ONT	6075425	-80.65	51.27	10	-10.4	-9.8	-0.6	1
4989	1920-12-27	MOOSONEE	ONT	6075425	-80.65	51.27	10	-19.9	-18.7	-1.2	1
4990	1930-10-29	MOOSONEE	ONT	6075425	-80.65	51.27	10	4.9	5.1	-0.2	1
4991	1931-05-02	MOOSONEE	ONT	6075425	-80.65	51.27	10	-1.6	-1.5	-0.1	1
4992	1936-11-20	MOOSONEE	ONT	6075425	-80.65	51.27	10	2	2.1	-0.1	1
4993	1936-12-23	MOOSONEE	ONT	6075425	-80.65	51.27	10	-22.2	-20.6	-1.6	1
4994	1937-02-01	MOOSONEE	ONT	6075425	-80.65	51.27	10	-16.2	-15.6	-0.6	1
4995	1937-12-09	MOOSONEE	ONT	6075425	-80.65	51.27	10	-11.9	-11.5	-0.4	1
4996	1938-01-17	MOOSONEE	ONT	6075425	-80.65	51.27	10	-13.5	-10.6	-2.9	1
4997	1938-02-14	MOOSONEE	ONT	6075425	-80.65	51.27	10	-22.2	-21.9	-0.3	1

4998	1938-09-19	MOOSONEE	ONT	6075425	-80.65	51.27	10	10.5	10.9	-0.4	1
4999	1938-12-05	MOOSONEE	ONT	6075425	-80.65	51.27	10	-0.7	-0.2	-0.5	1
5000	1941-01-18	MOOSONEE	ONT	6075425	-80.65	51.27	10	-17.4	-16.8	-0.6	1
5001	1943-10-18	MOOSONEE	ONT	6075425	-80.65	51.27	10	3.8	4	-0.2	1
5002	1947-03-01	MOOSONEE	ONT	6075425	-80.65	51.27	10	-7.4	-7.3	-0.1	1
5003	1953-02-16	MOOSONEE	ONT	6075425	-80.65	51.27	10	-13	-12.9	-0.1	1
5004	2008-02-18	MOOSONEE	ONT	6075425	-80.65	51.27	10	-15	-12.5	-2.5	1
5005	1993-11-03	FAIRVIEW	ALTA	3072525	-118.38	56.07	655	-6	-5.3	-0.7	1
5006	1993-12-31	FAIRVIEW	ALTA	3072525	-118.38	56.07	655	-16.5	-15.6	-0.9	1
5007	1994-01-05	FAIRVIEW	ALTA	3072525	-118.38	56.07	655	-25.5	-24.2	-1.3	1
5008	1994-01-13	FAIRVIEW	ALTA	3072525	-118.38	56.07	655	-22	-21.8	-0.2	1
5009	1994-01-14	FAIRVIEW	ALTA	3072525	-118.38	56.07	655	-21.5	-21.1	-0.4	1
5010	1994-01-15	FAIRVIEW	ALTA	3072525	-118.38	56.07	655	-22.5	-21.5	-1	1
5011	1994-02-20	FAIRVIEW	ALTA	3072525	-118.38	56.07	655	-26.5	-24.3	-2.2	1
5012	1994-11-01	FAIRVIEW	ALTA	3072525	-118.38	56.07	655	-5	-4.5	-0.5	1
5013	1994-12-01	FAIRVIEW	ALTA	3072525	-118.38	56.07	655	-21.5	-20.3	-1.2	1
5014	1995-10-16	FAIRVIEW	ALTA	3072525	-118.38	56.07	655	0	0.6	-0.6	1
5015	1995-11-07	FAIRVIEW	ALTA	3072525	-118.38	56.07	655	-12	-10.7	-1.3	1
5016	1996-01-13	FAIRVIEW	ALTA	3072525	-118.38	56.07	655	-26	-23	-3	1
5017	1997-01-21	FAIRVIEW	ALTA	3072525	-118.38	56.07	655	-15.5	-14.6	-0.9	1
5018	1998-01-19	FAIRVIEW	ALTA	3072525	-118.38	56.07	655	-13.9	-12.3	-1.6	1
5019	1998-10-07	FAIRVIEW	ALTA	3072525	-118.38	56.07	655	6.4	6.9	-0.5	1
5020	1998-10-09	FAIRVIEW	ALTA	3072525	-118.38	56.07	655	0.3	0.9	-0.6	1
5021	1998-11-15	FAIRVIEW	ALTA	3072525	-118.38	56.07	655	-10.1	-10	-0.1	1
5022	1998-12-03	FAIRVIEW	ALTA	3072525	-118.38	56.07	655	-7.5	-7	-0.5	1
5023	1998-12-17	FAIRVIEW	ALTA	3072525	-118.38	56.07	655	-11.9	-9.6	-2.3	1
5024	1998-12-18	FAIRVIEW	ALTA	3072525	-118.38	56.07	655	-19.7	-18.2	-1.5	1
5025	1999-01-05	FAIRVIEW	ALTA	3072525	-118.38	56.07	655	-17	-15.2	-1.8	1
5026	1999-01-10	FAIRVIEW	ALTA	3072525	-118.38	56.07	655	-20.2	-19.2	-1	1
5027	1999-01-22	FAIRVIEW	ALTA	3072525	-118.38	56.07	655	-19.4	-18.6	-0.8	1
5028	2008-12-22	FAIRVIEW	ALTA	3072525	-118.38	56.07	655	-30	-28	-2	1
5029	2008-12-23	FAIRVIEW	ALTA	3072525	-118.38	56.07	655	-24.9	-22.4	-2.5	1
5030	1927-01-16	JASPER	ALTA	3053536	-118.03	52.93	1020	-15	-9.1	-5.9	1
5031	2003-04-13	JASPER	ALTA	3053536	-118.03	52.93	1020	1.9	3.7	-1.8	1

5032	1922-10-31	ATHABASCA	ALTA	3060L20	-113.53	54.82	515	-0.9	-0.2	-0.7	1
5033	1924-05-18	ATHABASCA	ALTA	3060L20	-113.53	54.82	515	-0.4	0.7	-1.1	1
5034	1924-10-03	ATHABASCA	ALTA	3060L20	-113.53	54.82	515	6.6	6.7	-0.1	1
5035	1924-12-14	ATHABASCA	ALTA	3060L20	-113.53	54.82	515	-27.9	-27	-0.9	1
5036	1926-09-15	ATHABASCA	ALTA	3060L20	-113.53	54.82	515	-0.4	0	-0.4	1
5037	1930-02-07	ATHABASCA	ALTA	3060L20	-113.53	54.82	515	-7.6	-6.3	-1.3	1
5038	1932-01-12	ATHABASCA	ALTA	3060L20	-113.53	54.82	515	-1.9	0	-1.9	1
5039	1932-11-16	ATHABASCA	ALTA	3060L20	-113.53	54.82	515	-19.8	-19.3	-0.5	1
5040	1933-10-20	ATHABASCA	ALTA	3060L20	-113.53	54.82	515	-6.8	-6.2	-0.6	1
5041	1933-12-03	ATHABASCA	ALTA	3060L20	-113.53	54.82	515	-1.9	-1.7	-0.2	1
5042	1935-01-29	ATHABASCA	ALTA	3060L20	-113.53	54.82	515	3.5	5.7	-2.2	1
5043	1935-03-10	ATHABASCA	ALTA	3060L20	-113.53	54.82	515	-3.4	-3.2	-0.2	1
5044	1935-11-30	ATHABASCA	ALTA	3060L20	-113.53	54.82	515	-1.9	-1.7	-0.2	1
5045	1938-01-19	ATHABASCA	ALTA	3060L20	-113.53	54.82	515	-8.7	-8.2	-0.5	1
5046	1939-12-02	ATHABASCA	ALTA	3060L20	-113.53	54.82	515	0.1	0.8	-0.7	1
5047	1940-03-09	ATHABASCA	ALTA	3060L20	-113.53	54.82	515	-7.5	-6.3	-1.2	1
5048	1940-05-29	ATHABASCA	ALTA	3060L20	-113.53	54.82	515	0.1	2.8	-2.7	1
5049	1942-01-05	ATHABASCA	ALTA	3060L20	-113.53	54.82	515	-33.4	-32.3	-1.1	1
5050	1942-01-21	ATHABASCA	ALTA	3060L20	-113.53	54.82	515	-10.2	-9.6	-0.6	1
5051	1942-03-04	ATHABASCA	ALTA	3060L20	-113.53	54.82	515	1.8	3.5	-1.7	1
5052	1943-01-06	ATHABASCA	ALTA	3060L20	-113.53	54.82	515	-0.9	-0.3	-0.6	1
5053	1943-12-06	ATHABASCA	ALTA	3060L20	-113.53	54.82	515	-0.9	-0.4	-0.5	1
5054	1944-11-08	ATHABASCA	ALTA	3060L20	-113.53	54.82	515	-2.4	-2.3	-0.1	1
5055	1944-11-13	ATHABASCA	ALTA	3060L20	-113.53	54.82	515	-7.5	-6.1	-1.4	1
5056	1944-11-19	ATHABASCA	ALTA	3060L20	-113.53	54.82	515	-0.9	-0.3	-0.6	1
5057	1944-11-23	ATHABASCA	ALTA	3060L20	-113.53	54.82	515	-1.5	-0.3	-1.2	1
5058	1944-11-24	ATHABASCA	ALTA	3060L20	-113.53	54.82	515	-7.5	-6.2	-1.3	1
5059	1944-11-30	ATHABASCA	ALTA	3060L20	-113.53	54.82	515	-12.6	-12.5	-0.1	1
5060	1945-02-15	ATHABASCA	ALTA	3060L20	-113.53	54.82	515	-30.7	-30.1	-0.6	1
5061	1945-04-15	ATHABASCA	ALTA	3060L20	-113.53	54.82	515	3.6	4.8	-1.2	1
5062	1946-08-06	ATHABASCA	ALTA	3060L20	-113.53	54.82	515	18	18.6	-0.6	1
5063	1946-09-21	ATHABASCA	ALTA	3060L20	-113.53	54.82	515	6.6	8	-1.4	1
5064	1947-04-01	ATHABASCA	ALTA	3060L20	-113.53	54.82	515	-1.9	-1.7	-0.2	1
5065	1949-01-18	ATHABASCA	ALTA	3060L20	-113.53	54.82	515	-27.9	-27	-0.9	1

5066	1949-11-25	ATHABASCA	ALTA	3060L20	-113.53	54.82	515	-0.9	0.8	-1.7	1
5067	1949-12-29	ATHABASCA	ALTA	3060L20	-113.53	54.82	515	-25.1	-23.5	-1.6	1
5068	1949-12-31	ATHABASCA	ALTA	3060L20	-113.53	54.82	515	-27.9	-26	-1.9	1
5069	1950-01-22	ATHABASCA	ALTA	3060L20	-113.53	54.82	515	-26.2	-26	-0.2	1
5070	1950-10-01	ATHABASCA	ALTA	3060L20	-113.53	54.82	515	3	3.5	-0.5	1
5071	1950-12-13	ATHABASCA	ALTA	3060L20	-113.53	54.82	515	-10.2	-9.5	-0.7	1
5072	1951-07-12	ATHABASCA	ALTA	3060L20	-113.53	54.82	515	15	15.9	-0.9	1
5073	1951-10-14	ATHABASCA	ALTA	3060L20	-113.53	54.82	515	-1.9	-1.7	-0.2	1
5074	1951-11-10	ATHABASCA	ALTA	3060L20	-113.53	54.82	515	-0.9	0.8	-1.7	1
5075	1951-12-11	ATHABASCA	ALTA	3060L20	-113.53	54.82	515	-2.8	-2.3	-0.5	1
5076	1952-01-08	ATHABASCA	ALTA	3060L20	-113.53	54.82	515	-25.1	-23.7	-1.4	1
5077	1952-06-11	ATHABASCA	ALTA	3060L20	-113.53	54.82	515	9.4	10.4	-1	1
5078	1952-09-11	ATHABASCA	ALTA	3060L20	-113.53	54.82	515	8.8	9.4	-0.6	1
5079	1952-11-15	ATHABASCA	ALTA	3060L20	-113.53	54.82	515	0.7	1.6	-0.9	1
5080	1953-12-21	ATHABASCA	ALTA	3060L20	-113.53	54.82	515	-1.9	-1.7	-0.2	1
5081	1954-01-08	ATHABASCA	ALTA	3060L20	-113.53	54.82	515	-22.4	-21.4	-1	1
5082	1954-02-13	ATHABASCA	ALTA	3060L20	-113.53	54.82	515	-25.1	-23.8	-1.3	1
5083	1954-02-17	ATHABASCA	ALTA	3060L20	-113.53	54.82	515	-22.4	-21.6	-0.8	1
5084	1954-02-25	ATHABASCA	ALTA	3060L20	-113.53	54.82	515	0.1	1.6	-1.5	1
5085	1954-09-15	ATHABASCA	ALTA	3060L20	-113.53	54.82	515	7.3	8.6	-1.3	1
5086	1954-09-19	ATHABASCA	ALTA	3060L20	-113.53	54.82	515	4.2	4.8	-0.6	1
5087	1955-04-28	ATHABASCA	ALTA	3060L20	-113.53	54.82	515	0.1	1.6	-1.5	1
5088	1955-05-12	ATHABASCA	ALTA	3060L20	-113.53	54.82	515	6.1	6.7	-0.6	1
5089	1955-09-20	ATHABASCA	ALTA	3060L20	-113.53	54.82	515	6.1	6.3	-0.2	1
5090	1955-11-10	ATHABASCA	ALTA	3060L20	-113.53	54.82	515	-5	-3.6	-1.4	1
5091	1955-12-11	ATHABASCA	ALTA	3060L20	-113.53	54.82	515	-22.9	-21.8	-1.1	1
5092	1955-12-23	ATHABASCA	ALTA	3060L20	-113.53	54.82	515	-28.4	-27	-1.4	1
5093	1956-03-26	ATHABASCA	ALTA	3060L20	-113.53	54.82	515	-0.4	-0.1	-0.3	1
5094	1956-09-01	ATHABASCA	ALTA	3060L20	-113.53	54.82	515	4.2	6.3	-2.1	1
5095	1956-12-17	ATHABASCA	ALTA	3060L20	-113.53	54.82	515	-30.7	-30.1	-0.6	1
5096	1956-12-24	ATHABASCA	ALTA	3060L20	-113.53	54.82	515	0.7	1.6	-0.9	1
5097	1957-11-14	ATHABASCA	ALTA	3060L20	-113.53	54.82	515	-2.8	-2.7	-0.1	1
5098	1957-12-09	ATHABASCA	ALTA	3060L20	-113.53	54.82	515	-0.9	0.1	-1	1
5099	1958-03-26	ATHABASCA	ALTA	3060L20	-113.53	54.82	515	-3.9	-3.6	-0.3	1

5100	1958-09-13	ATHABASCA	ALTA	3060L20	-113.53	54.82	515	10	10.4	-0.4	1
5101	1988-12-22	GRAND RAPIDS	MAN	5031111	-99.28	53.15	223	-13.5	-12.5	-1	1
5102	1988-12-24	GRAND RAPIDS	MAN	5031111	-99.28	53.15	223	-22.5	-19.5	-3	1
5103	2009-07-29	GRAND RAPIDS	MAN	5031111	-99.28	53.15	223	12.5	13	-0.5	1
5104	2010-11-16	GRAND RAPIDS	MAN	5031111	-99.28	53.15	223	-4.5	-1	-3.5	1
5105	2012-04-25	GRAND RAPIDS	MAN	5031111	-99.28	53.15	223	2	5	-3	1
5106	2012-12-17	GRAND RAPIDS	MAN	5031111	-99.28	53.15	223	-18	-16	-2	1
5107	2013-11-10	GRAND RAPIDS	MAN	5031111	-99.28	53.15	223	-15	-11	-4	1
5108	2016-12-23	GRAND RAPIDS	MAN	5031111	-99.28	53.15	223	-17	-5	-12	1
5109	2017-03-20	GRAND RAPIDS	MAN	5031111	-99.28	53.15	223	-7	-4	-3	1
5110	2017-11-24	GRAND RAPIDS	MAN	5031111	-99.28	53.15	223	-12	-7	-5	1
5111	2017-12-04	GRAND RAPIDS	MAN	5031111	-99.28	53.15	223	-12	-11	-1	1
5112	1992-12-19	CHIBOUGAMAU	QUE	7091404	-74.85	49.78	387	-8.8	-8.2	-0.6	1
5113	1992-12-25	CHIBOUGAMAU	QUE	7091404	-74.85	49.78	387	-21.6	-19	-2.6	1
5114	1993-10-27	CHIBOUGAMAU	QUE	7091404	-74.85	49.78	387	-2	-1.6	-0.4	1
5115	1993-10-30	CHIBOUGAMAU	QUE	7091404	-74.85	49.78	387	-4.2	-1.1	-3.1	1
5116	1993-12-12	CHIBOUGAMAU	QUE	7091404	-74.85	49.78	387	-12.4	-10.9	-1.5	1
5117	1994-12-18	CHIBOUGAMAU	QUE	7091404	-74.85	49.78	387	-11.1	-1.6	-9.5	1
5118	2012-11-24	CHIBOUGAMAU	QUE	7091404	-74.85	49.78	387	-8.2	-4.3	-3.9	1
5119	2012-12-14	CHIBOUGAMAU	QUE	7091404	-74.85	49.78	387	-22	-13	-9	1
5120	2012-12-26	CHIBOUGAMAU	QUE	7091404	-74.85	49.78	387	-16.2	-15	-1.2	1
5121	2013-01-25	CHIBOUGAMAU	QUE	7091404	-74.85	49.78	387	-19.7	-19.4	-0.3	1
5122	2013-01-26	CHIBOUGAMAU	QUE	7091404	-74.85	49.78	387	-23.2	-13.5	-9.7	1
5123	2013-01-27	CHIBOUGAMAU	QUE	7091404	-74.85	49.78	387	-13	-6.4	-6.6	1
5124	1881-11-17	BAGOTVILLE	QUE	7060400	-71	48.33	159	-8.3	-7.8	-0.5	1
5125	1882-01-07	BAGOTVILLE	QUE	7060400	-71	48.33	159	-9	-8.9	-0.1	1
5126	1884-12-07	BAGOTVILLE	QUE	7060400	-71	48.33	159	-2.2	-2.1	-0.1	1
5127	1885-02-25	BAGOTVILLE	QUE	7060400	-71	48.33	159	-11.5	-10.3	-1.2	1
5128	1888-03-05	BAGOTVILLE	QUE	7060400	-71	48.33	159	-10.8	-9.8	-1	1
5129	1890-01-16	BAGOTVILLE	QUE	7060400	-71	48.33	159	-9.5	-9.1	-0.4	1
5130	1890-03-15	BAGOTVILLE	QUE	7060400	-71	48.33	159	-7.8	-5.8	-2	1
5131	1890-11-06	BAGOTVILLE	QUE	7060400	-71	48.33	159	-2.8	-2.5	-0.3	1
5132	1890-11-14	BAGOTVILLE	QUE	7060400	-71	48.33	159	-2.2	-1.9	-0.3	1
5133	1890-11-22	BAGOTVILLE	QUE	7060400	-71	48.33	159	-10	-8.4	-1.6	1

5134	1890-11-23	BAGOTVILLE	QUE	7060400	-71	48.33	159	-6.4	-6.3	-0.1	1
5135	1896-11-01	BAGOTVILLE	QUE	7060400	-71	48.33	159	-2.8	-2.1	-0.7	1
5136	1898-01-26	BAGOTVILLE	QUE	7060400	-71	48.33	159	-11.5	-11.4	-0.1	1
5137	1898-11-23	BAGOTVILLE	QUE	7060400	-71	48.33	159	3	3.2	-0.2	1
5138	1905-12-23	BAGOTVILLE	QUE	7060400	-71	48.33	159	-10	-8.7	-1.3	1
5139	1910-01-25	BAGOTVILLE	QUE	7060400	-71	48.33	159	-10.4	-9	-1.4	1
5140	1912-12-10	BAGOTVILLE	QUE	7060400	-71	48.33	159	-11.9	-11.4	-0.5	1
5141	1914-01-27	BAGOTVILLE	QUE	7060400	-71	48.33	159	-9	-8.7	-0.3	1
5142	1914-11-10	BAGOTVILLE	QUE	7060400	-71	48.33	159	-10	-9.4	-0.6	1
5143	1917-10-30	BAGOTVILLE	QUE	7060400	-71	48.33	159	3	3.5	-0.5	1
5144	1917-11-22	BAGOTVILLE	QUE	7060400	-71	48.33	159	-2.2	-2.1	-0.1	1
5145	1920-03-29	BAGOTVILLE	QUE	7060400	-71	48.33	159	-3.3	-2.1	-1.2	1
5146	1922-04-07	BAGOTVILLE	QUE	7060400	-71	48.33	159	2.9	3.2	-0.3	1
5147	1922-10-27	BAGOTVILLE	QUE	7060400	-71	48.33	159	-2.2	-2.1	-0.1	1
5148	1924-04-05	BAGOTVILLE	QUE	7060400	-71	48.33	159	-2.2	-1.7	-0.5	1
5149	1924-05-19	BAGOTVILLE	QUE	7060400	-71	48.33	159	2.5	2.7	-0.2	1
5150	1925-10-24	BAGOTVILLE	QUE	7060400	-71	48.33	159	-2.2	-2.1	-0.1	1
5151	1925-12-28	BAGOTVILLE	QUE	7060400	-71	48.33	159	-11	-10.9	-0.1	1
5152	1930-11-25	BAGOTVILLE	QUE	7060400	-71	48.33	159	-2.8	-2.1	-0.7	1
5153	1930-12-07	BAGOTVILLE	QUE	7060400	-71	48.33	159	-2.2	-1.6	-0.6	1
5154	1930-12-20	BAGOTVILLE	QUE	7060400	-71	48.33	159	-4.3	-3.3	-1	1
5155	1930-12-21	BAGOTVILLE	QUE	7060400	-71	48.33	159	-4.3	-3.3	-1	1
5156	1982-12-02	STEPHENVILLE	NFLD	8403801	-58.55	48.53	25	-10.8	10.8	-21.6	1
5157	1993-01-28	STEPHENVILLE	NFLD	8403801	-58.55	48.53	25	-7.8	-6.7	-1.1	1
5158	1993-11-24	DEWAR LAKES	NU	2401030	-71.17	68.65	527	-25.7	-25	-0.7	1
5159	1994-04-15	DEWAR LAKES	NU	2401030	-71.17	68.65	527	-20.4	-17.4	-3	1
5160	1994-05-15	DEWAR LAKES	NU	2401030	-71.17	68.65	527	-2.9	-1.9	-1	1
5161	1994-10-13	DEWAR LAKES	NU	2401030	-71.17	68.65	527	-11.9	-8.3	-3.6	1
5162	1994-12-28	DEWAR LAKES	NU	2401030	-71.17	68.65	527	-21.7	-19.9	-1.8	1
5163	2010-04-15	DEWAR LAKES	NU	2401030	-71.17	68.65	527	-13.9	-12.3	-1.6	1
5164	1896-01-09	MOOSE JAW	SASK	4015322	-105.55	50.33	577	0.1	5.1	-5	1
5165	1896-01-10	MOOSE JAW	SASK	4015322	-105.55	50.33	577	-4.8	-2.7	-2.1	1
5166	1896-01-13	MOOSE JAW	SASK	4015322	-105.55	50.33	577	-19.2	-14	-5.2	1
5167	1896-01-14	MOOSE JAW	SASK	4015322	-105.55	50.33	577	-32.2	-19.3	-12.9	1

5168	1896-01-19	MOOSE JAW	SASK	4015322	-105.55	50.33	577	-14.8	-10.8	-4	1
5169	1896-11-26	MOOSE JAW	SASK	4015322	-105.55	50.33	577	-22.1	-21.8	-0.3	1
5170	1900-11-19	MOOSE JAW	SASK	4015322	-105.55	50.33	577	-22.1	-21.8	-0.3	1
5171	1901-02-10	MOOSE JAW	SASK	4015322	-105.55	50.33	577	-22.1	-21.7	-0.4	1
5172	1909-01-07	MOOSE JAW	SASK	4015322	-105.55	50.33	577	-36.2	-35.3	-0.9	1
5173	1909-02-15	MOOSE JAW	SASK	4015322	-105.55	50.33	577	-19.8	-19.6	-0.2	1
5174	1910-02-15	MOOSE JAW	SASK	4015322	-105.55	50.33	577	-22.2	-21.6	-0.6	1
5175	1916-01-27	MOOSE JAW	SASK	4015322	-105.55	50.33	577	-27.3	-27	-0.3	1
5176	1916-01-29	MOOSE JAW	SASK	4015322	-105.55	50.33	577	-25.6	-25.4	-0.2	1
5177	1916-12-27	MOOSE JAW	SASK	4015322	-105.55	50.33	577	-24	-23.2	-0.8	1
5178	1917-12-26	MOOSE JAW	SASK	4015322	-105.55	50.33	577	-26.7	-26	-0.7	1
5179	1924-12-15	MOOSE JAW	SASK	4015322	-105.55	50.33	577	-28	-26.8	-1.2	1
5180	1925-09-29	MOOSE JAW	SASK	4015322	-105.55	50.33	577	1.4	1.5	-0.1	1
5181	1926-12-12	MOOSE JAW	SASK	4015322	-105.55	50.33	577	-26.4	-26.2	-0.2	1
5182	1939-03-13	MOOSE JAW	SASK	4015322	-105.55	50.33	577	-15.2	-14.8	-0.4	1
5183	1975-02-14	KUUIJUAPIK	QUE	7103536	-77.75	55.28	12	-20.6	-20.5	-0.1	1
5184	1989-06-09	CAPE HOOPER	NU	2400660	-66.82	68.47	390	-3.5	-2.4	-1.1	1
5185	1994-03-04	CAPE HOOPER	NU	2400660	-66.82	68.47	390	-31.8	-31.7	-0.1	1
5186	1994-04-09	CAPE HOOPER	NU	2400660	-66.82	68.47	390	-20.9	-17.8	-3.1	1
5187	1994-04-14	CAPE HOOPER	NU	2400660	-66.82	68.47	390	-21.6	-20.2	-1.4	1
5188	1994-04-18	CAPE HOOPER	NU	2400660	-66.82	68.47	390	-16.7	-14.6	-2.1	1
5189	1994-04-19	CAPE HOOPER	NU	2400660	-66.82	68.47	390	-12.8	-8.3	-4.5	1
5190	1994-04-20	CAPE HOOPER	NU	2400660	-66.82	68.47	390	-7.7	-6.4	-1.3	1
5191	1994-05-28	CAPE HOOPER	NU	2400660	-66.82	68.47	390	-3	1.2	-4.2	1
5192	2010-04-20	CAPE HOOPER	NU	2400660	-66.82	68.47	390	-11.7	-9.3	-2.4	1
5193	2010-04-21	CAPE HOOPER	NU	2400660	-66.82	68.47	390	-13	-8.5	-4.5	1
5194	1984-01-18	WELLAND	ONT	6139449	-79.27	43	178	-12	-11	-1	1
5195	1984-01-30	WELLAND	ONT	6139449	-79.27	43	178	-7	-4	-3	1
5196	2007-10-23	WELLAND	ONT	6139449	-79.27	43	178	10	15	-5	1
5197	2008-02-05	WELLAND	ONT	6139449	-79.27	43	178	0	5	-5	1
5198	2008-02-09	WELLAND	ONT	6139449	-79.27	43	178	-5	-1.5	-3.5	1
5199	2010-01-19	WELLAND	ONT	6139449	-79.27	43	178	-5	-3	-2	1
5200	2010-01-20	WELLAND	ONT	6139449	-79.27	43	178	-8.5	-5	-3.5	1
5201	2013-01-14	WELLAND	ONT	6139449	-79.27	43	178	-2	-1	-1	1

5202	2013-08-13	WELLAND	ONT	6139449	-79.27	43	178	17	18	-1	1
5203	2013-07-26	INUKJUAQ	QUE	710S005	-78.08	58.47	26	10.2	11.5	-1.3	1
5204	1913-12-28	FAUQUIER	BC	1142820	-118.07	49.87	490	1.2	1.3	-0.1	1
5205	1914-01-17	FAUQUIER	BC	1142820	-118.07	49.87	490	-1	0.7	-1.7	1
5206	1914-01-18	FAUQUIER	BC	1142820	-118.07	49.87	490	-1	-0.4	-0.6	1
5207	1914-01-21	FAUQUIER	BC	1142820	-118.07	49.87	490	-2.1	-0.9	-1.2	1
5208	1914-01-26	FAUQUIER	BC	1142820	-118.07	49.87	490	-3.3	-3	-0.3	1
5209	1914-11-05	FAUQUIER	BC	1142820	-118.07	49.87	490	4.9	5.8	-0.9	1
5210	1914-11-18	FAUQUIER	BC	1142820	-118.07	49.87	490	-1	-0.9	-0.1	1
5211	1914-11-19	FAUQUIER	BC	1142820	-118.07	49.87	490	0.1	0.7	-0.6	1
5212	1914-12-05	FAUQUIER	BC	1142820	-118.07	49.87	490	-2.1	-0.9	-1.2	1
5213	1914-12-06	FAUQUIER	BC	1142820	-118.07	49.87	490	-1.6	-0.9	-0.7	1
5214	1914-12-07	FAUQUIER	BC	1142820	-118.07	49.87	490	-1.6	-0.9	-0.7	1
5215	1914-12-09	FAUQUIER	BC	1142820	-118.07	49.87	490	-3.3	-3	-0.3	1
5216	1914-12-10	FAUQUIER	BC	1142820	-118.07	49.87	490	-5.4	-4.3	-1.1	1
5217	1914-12-25	FAUQUIER	BC	1142820	-118.07	49.87	490	-3.3	-3	-0.3	1
5218	1914-12-30	FAUQUIER	BC	1142820	-118.07	49.87	490	-1	-0.4	-0.6	1
5219	1915-02-02	FAUQUIER	BC	1142820	-118.07	49.87	490	0.1	0.2	-0.1	1
5220	1915-02-06	FAUQUIER	BC	1142820	-118.07	49.87	490	-0.4	0.2	-0.6	1
5221	1915-02-08	FAUQUIER	BC	1142820	-118.07	49.87	490	0.7	1.3	-0.6	1
5222	1915-04-30	FAUQUIER	BC	1142820	-118.07	49.87	490	4.8	5.8	-1	1
5223	1916-01-09	FAUQUIER	BC	1142820	-118.07	49.87	490	-13.3	-12.5	-0.8	1
5224	1916-01-24	FAUQUIER	BC	1142820	-118.07	49.87	490	-10	-9.8	-0.2	1
5225	1921-10-31	FAUQUIER	BC	1142820	-118.07	49.87	490	9.8	10.4	-0.6	1
5226	1921-11-17	FAUQUIER	BC	1142820	-118.07	49.87	490	-1	-0.9	-0.1	1
5227	1921-11-21	FAUQUIER	BC	1142820	-118.07	49.87	490	-8.9	-8.1	-0.8	1
5228	1921-11-25	FAUQUIER	BC	1142820	-118.07	49.87	490	1.2	1.3	-0.1	1
5229	1921-11-26	FAUQUIER	BC	1142820	-118.07	49.87	490	0.7	1.6	-0.9	1
5230	1921-11-29	FAUQUIER	BC	1142820	-118.07	49.87	490	1.1	1.3	-0.2	1
5231	1921-12-05	FAUQUIER	BC	1142820	-118.07	49.87	490	-1	-0.4	-0.6	1
5232	1921-12-07	FAUQUIER	BC	1142820	-118.07	49.87	490	0.7	1.3	-0.6	1
5233	1921-12-09	FAUQUIER	BC	1142820	-118.07	49.87	490	1.2	1.3	-0.1	1
5234	1921-12-18	FAUQUIER	BC	1142820	-118.07	49.87	490	-6.7	-5.4	-1.3	1
5235	1922-03-04	FAUQUIER	BC	1142820	-118.07	49.87	490	1.1	1.3	-0.2	1

5236	1922-10-27	FAUQUIER	BC	1142820	-118.07	49.87	490	7.9	8.8	-0.9	1
5237	1922-11-23	FAUQUIER	BC	1142820	-118.07	49.87	490	1.1	1.7	-0.6	1
5238	1922-11-24	FAUQUIER	BC	1142820	-118.07	49.87	490	0.1	0.7	-0.6	1
5239	1922-11-28	FAUQUIER	BC	1142820	-118.07	49.87	490	0.7	1.3	-0.6	1
5240	1922-12-02	FAUQUIER	BC	1142820	-118.07	49.87	490	-2.1	-1.5	-0.6	1
5241	1922-12-04	FAUQUIER	BC	1142820	-118.07	49.87	490	-3.3	-3	-0.3	1
5242	1922-12-10	FAUQUIER	BC	1142820	-118.07	49.87	490	-9.4	-8.1	-1.3	1
5243	1922-12-21	FAUQUIER	BC	1142820	-118.07	49.87	490	0.1	0.2	-0.1	1
5244	1922-12-22	FAUQUIER	BC	1142820	-118.07	49.87	490	-0.4	0.2	-0.6	1
5245	1922-12-31	FAUQUIER	BC	1142820	-118.07	49.87	490	0.1	0.2	-0.1	1
5246	1923-01-03	FAUQUIER	BC	1142820	-118.07	49.87	490	-1	0.7	-1.7	1
5247	1923-01-05	FAUQUIER	BC	1142820	-118.07	49.87	490	0.1	0.2	-0.1	1
5248	1923-01-10	FAUQUIER	BC	1142820	-118.07	49.87	490	0.7	1.3	-0.6	1
5249	1923-01-19	FAUQUIER	BC	1142820	-118.07	49.87	490	-0.4	0.2	-0.6	1
5250	1923-02-05	FAUQUIER	BC	1142820	-118.07	49.87	490	-6.1	-5.9	-0.2	1
5251	1923-02-12	FAUQUIER	BC	1142820	-118.07	49.87	490	-13.3	-11.9	-1.4	1
5252	1923-02-13	FAUQUIER	BC	1142820	-118.07	49.87	490	-13.3	-10.9	-2.4	1
5253	1923-11-09	FAUQUIER	BC	1142820	-118.07	49.87	490	1.8	2	-0.2	1
5254	1923-11-10	FAUQUIER	BC	1142820	-118.07	49.87	490	1.1	1.3	-0.2	1
5255	1923-11-11	FAUQUIER	BC	1142820	-118.07	49.87	490	0.7	1.3	-0.6	1
5256	1923-12-28	FAUQUIER	BC	1142820	-118.07	49.87	490	-1	-0.4	-0.6	1
5257	1925-08-22	FAUQUIER	BC	1142820	-118.07	49.87	490	9.4	9.9	-0.5	1
5258	1925-12-27	FAUQUIER	BC	1142820	-118.07	49.87	490	1.2	1.3	-0.1	1
5259	1926-10-16	FAUQUIER	BC	1142820	-118.07	49.87	490	9.8	10.4	-0.6	1
5260	1927-02-15	FAUQUIER	BC	1142820	-118.07	49.87	490	-3.8	-2.5	-1.3	1
5261	1927-11-21	FAUQUIER	BC	1142820	-118.07	49.87	490	1.1	1.3	-0.2	1
5262	1927-12-28	FAUQUIER	BC	1142820	-118.07	49.87	490	-1	0.2	-1.2	1
5263	1928-11-10	FAUQUIER	BC	1142820	-118.07	49.87	490	3.6	3.9	-0.3	1
5264	1928-11-25	FAUQUIER	BC	1142820	-118.07	49.87	490	1.2	1.3	-0.1	1
5265	1928-12-03	FAUQUIER	BC	1142820	-118.07	49.87	490	-5.4	-4.8	-0.6	1
5266	1928-12-21	FAUQUIER	BC	1142820	-118.07	49.87	490	-2.8	-2.5	-0.3	1
5267	1929-01-18	FAUQUIER	BC	1142820	-118.07	49.87	490	-4.9	-4.3	-0.6	1
5268	1929-04-29	FAUQUIER	BC	1142820	-118.07	49.87	490	8.1	8.8	-0.7	1
5269	1929-12-04	FAUQUIER	BC	1142820	-118.07	49.87	490	-1	-0.4	-0.6	1

5270	1929-12-08	FAUQUIER	BC	1142820	-118.07	49.87	490	-2.1	-1.5	-0.6	1
5271	1929-12-11	FAUQUIER	BC	1142820	-118.07	49.87	490	-7.8	-7.6	-0.2	1
5272	1929-12-18	FAUQUIER	BC	1142820	-118.07	49.87	490	-3.8	-3.6	-0.2	1
5273	1930-01-05	FAUQUIER	BC	1142820	-118.07	49.87	490	-6.1	-5.4	-0.7	1
5274	1930-11-27	FAUQUIER	BC	1142820	-118.07	49.87	490	-2.8	-2.5	-0.3	1
5275	1930-12-11	FAUQUIER	BC	1142820	-118.07	49.87	490	0.1	0.2	-0.1	1
5276	1930-12-14	FAUQUIER	BC	1142820	-118.07	49.87	490	-0.4	0.2	-0.6	1
5277	1930-12-26	FAUQUIER	BC	1142820	-118.07	49.87	490	-2.1	0.2	-2.3	1
5278	1930-12-27	FAUQUIER	BC	1142820	-118.07	49.87	490	-1.6	0.2	-1.8	1
5279	1930-12-28	FAUQUIER	BC	1142820	-118.07	49.87	490	-2.1	0.2	-2.3	1
5280	1930-12-29	FAUQUIER	BC	1142820	-118.07	49.87	490	-3.3	-2.5	-0.8	1
5281	1931-01-18	FAUQUIER	BC	1142820	-118.07	49.87	490	0.1	0.2	-0.1	1
5282	1931-01-26	FAUQUIER	BC	1142820	-118.07	49.87	490	0.1	0.2	-0.1	1
5283	1931-01-29	FAUQUIER	BC	1142820	-118.07	49.87	490	-0.4	1.3	-1.7	1
5284	1931-01-31	FAUQUIER	BC	1142820	-118.07	49.87	490	0.7	1.7	-1	1
5285	1931-02-02	FAUQUIER	BC	1142820	-118.07	49.87	490	0.1	0.2	-0.1	1
5286	1931-12-07	FAUQUIER	BC	1142820	-118.07	49.87	490	-2.1	-0.4	-1.7	1
5287	1931-12-21	FAUQUIER	BC	1142820	-118.07	49.87	490	0.1	0.2	-0.1	1
5288	1933-12-09	FAUQUIER	BC	1142820	-118.07	49.87	490	-2.1	-0.4	-1.7	1
5289	1934-09-22	FAUQUIER	BC	1142820	-118.07	49.87	490	6.5	7	-0.5	1
5290	2009-12-07	FORT SIMPSON	NWT	2202103	-121.23	61.77	170	-11.5	-11.4	-0.1	1
5291	2009-12-09	FORT SIMPSON	NWT	2202103	-121.23	61.77	170	-11.2	-6.3	-4.9	1
5292	2018-12-23	FORT SIMPSON	NWT	2202103	-121.23	61.77	170	-26.4	-23.3	-3.1	1
5293	1962-04-28	SHEENBOROUGH	QUE	7038080	-77.32	45.95	137	6.9	7.9	-1	1
5294	1964-02-07	SHEENBOROUGH	QUE	7038080	-77.32	45.95	137	-4.3	-3.3	-1	1
5295	1964-02-13	SHEENBOROUGH	QUE	7038080	-77.32	45.95	137	-7	-3.9	-3.1	1
5296	1978-10-22	SHEENBOROUGH	QUE	7038080	-77.32	45.95	137	5.8	7.5	-1.7	1
5297	1987-03-05	SHEENBOROUGH	QUE	7038080	-77.32	45.95	137	2	18	-16	1
5298	2009-02-22	SHEENBOROUGH	QUE	7038080	-77.32	45.95	137	-9	-8	-1	1
5299	2010-11-23	SHEENBOROUGH	QUE	7038080	-77.32	45.95	137	-1	1	-2	1
5300	1984-11-14	PELLY	SASK	4086000	-101.87	52.08	509	-12	-11	-1	1
5301	1984-11-27	PELLY	SASK	4086000	-101.87	52.08	509	-9	-7.5	-1.5	1
5302	1984-11-28	PELLY	SASK	4086000	-101.87	52.08	509	-10.5	-10	-0.5	1
5303	2007-12-06	PELLY	SASK	4086000	-101.87	52.08	509	-20.5	-18	-2.5	1

5304	2007-12-21	PELLY	SASK	4086000	-101.87	52.08	509	-12.5	-10	-2.5	1
5305	2008-08-22	PELLY	SASK	4086000	-101.87	52.08	509	12.5	13.5	-1	1
5306	2011-03-17	PELLY	SASK	4086000	-101.87	52.08	509	-12	-11	-1	1
5307	2013-06-20	PELLY	SASK	4086000	-101.87	52.08	509	11	13	-2	1
5308	1921-01-29	MONT LAURIER	QUE	7035160	-75.55	46.57	244	-13.1	-11.8	-1.3	1
5309	1930-01-24	MONT LAURIER	QUE	7035160	-75.55	46.57	244	-12	-11.8	-0.2	1
5310	1935-11-11	MONT LAURIER	QUE	7035160	-75.55	46.57	244	3	3.4	-0.4	1
5311	1935-12-10	MONT LAURIER	QUE	7035160	-75.55	46.57	244	-1.4	-1.3	-0.1	1
5312	1935-12-11	MONT LAURIER	QUE	7035160	-75.55	46.57	244	-3.7	-3.5	-0.2	1
5313	1935-12-16	MONT LAURIER	QUE	7035160	-75.55	46.57	244	-7.1	-6.9	-0.2	1
5314	1937-11-21	MONT LAURIER	QUE	7035160	-75.55	46.57	244	-4.2	-4.1	-0.1	1
5315	1940-01-20	MONT LAURIER	QUE	7035160	-75.55	46.57	244	-11	-10.7	-0.3	1
5316	1940-11-18	MONT LAURIER	QUE	7035160	-75.55	46.57	244	0.3	0.5	-0.2	1
5317	1940-11-30	MONT LAURIER	QUE	7035160	-75.55	46.57	244	-11.6	-11.3	-0.3	1
5318	1940-12-29	MONT LAURIER	QUE	7035160	-75.55	46.57	244	1.4	1.5	-0.1	1
5319	1943-02-08	MONT LAURIER	QUE	7035160	-75.55	46.57	244	-11	-10.7	-0.3	1
5320	1945-11-14	MONT LAURIER	QUE	7035160	-75.55	46.57	244	3	3.4	-0.4	1
5321	1945-11-15	MONT LAURIER	QUE	7035160	-75.55	46.57	244	-6.6	-6.3	-0.3	1
5322	1946-12-27	MONT LAURIER	QUE	7035160	-75.55	46.57	244	-3.1	-3	-0.1	1
5323	1946-12-30	MONT LAURIER	QUE	7035160	-75.55	46.57	244	-11	-10.7	-0.3	1
5324	1947-01-28	MONT LAURIER	QUE	7035160	-75.55	46.57	244	-9.3	-8.3	-1	1
5325	1947-08-25	MONT LAURIER	QUE	7035160	-75.55	46.57	244	20.5	20.6	-0.1	1
5326	1947-11-12	MONT LAURIER	QUE	7035160	-75.55	46.57	244	-0.3	0.1	-0.4	1
5327	1947-12-18	MONT LAURIER	QUE	7035160	-75.55	46.57	244	-12.6	-11.3	-1.3	1
5328	1947-12-28	MONT LAURIER	QUE	7035160	-75.55	46.57	244	-18.7	-17.7	-1	1
5329	1948-01-21	MONT LAURIER	QUE	7035160	-75.55	46.57	244	-19.2	-11.8	-7.4	1
5330	1948-01-22	MONT LAURIER	QUE	7035160	-75.55	46.57	244	-17	-11.8	-5.2	1
5331	1948-02-11	MONT LAURIER	QUE	7035160	-75.55	46.57	244	-11.6	-11.3	-0.3	1
5332	1948-03-27	MONT LAURIER	QUE	7035160	-75.55	46.57	244	-3.1	-3	-0.1	1
5333	1948-05-08	MONT LAURIER	QUE	7035160	-75.55	46.57	244	7	7.1	-0.1	1
5334	1948-12-14	MONT LAURIER	QUE	7035160	-75.55	46.57	244	-6.6	-6.4	-0.2	1
5335	1949-01-10	MONT LAURIER	QUE	7035160	-75.55	46.57	244	-6	-5.3	-0.7	1
5336	1949-02-25	MONT LAURIER	QUE	7035160	-75.55	46.57	244	-7.1	-1.9	-5.2	1
5337	1949-03-12	MONT LAURIER	QUE	7035160	-75.55	46.57	244	-8.8	-8.3	-0.5	1

5338	1949-10-31	MONT LAURIER	QUE	7035160	-75.55	46.57	244	5.2	5.5	-0.3	1
5339	1949-11-05	MONT LAURIER	QUE	7035160	-75.55	46.57	244	-4.3	-3.5	-0.8	1
5340	1949-12-23	MONT LAURIER	QUE	7035160	-75.55	46.57	244	-3.7	-3	-0.7	1
5341	1950-01-23	MONT LAURIER	QUE	7035160	-75.55	46.57	244	-9.9	-8.7	-1.2	1
5342	1950-02-19	MONT LAURIER	QUE	7035160	-75.55	46.57	244	-13.1	-12.4	-0.7	1
5343	1950-12-12	MONT LAURIER	QUE	7035160	-75.55	46.57	244	-4.9	-4.8	-0.1	1
5344	1951-02-13	MONT LAURIER	QUE	7035160	-75.55	46.57	244	-9.9	-9.3	-0.6	1
5345	1951-11-16	MONT LAURIER	QUE	7035160	-75.55	46.57	244	-1.4	-0.9	-0.5	1
5346	1952-11-27	MONT LAURIER	QUE	7035160	-75.55	46.57	244	2	2.1	-0.1	1
5347	1952-12-26	MONT LAURIER	QUE	7035160	-75.55	46.57	244	-1.4	-0.9	-0.5	1
5348	1952-12-27	MONT LAURIER	QUE	7035160	-75.55	46.57	244	-17	-15.9	-1.1	1
5349	1953-03-14	MONT LAURIER	QUE	7035160	-75.55	46.57	244	0.9	1	-0.1	1
5350	1954-02-05	MONT LAURIER	QUE	7035160	-75.55	46.57	244	-3.7	-3	-0.7	1
5351	1954-02-06	MONT LAURIER	QUE	7035160	-75.55	46.57	244	-12	-10.7	-1.3	1
5352	1954-02-09	MONT LAURIER	QUE	7035160	-75.55	46.57	244	-6	-5.9	-0.1	1
5353	1954-02-21	MONT LAURIER	QUE	7035160	-75.55	46.57	244	4.6	5	-0.4	1
5354	1954-03-04	MONT LAURIER	QUE	7035160	-75.55	46.57	244	-12	-11.8	-0.2	1
5355	1954-11-21	MONT LAURIER	QUE	7035160	-75.55	46.57	244	-1.4	-1.3	-0.1	1
5356	1954-12-02	MONT LAURIER	QUE	7035160	-75.55	46.57	244	-10.5	-10.3	-0.2	1
5357	1954-12-07	MONT LAURIER	QUE	7035160	-75.55	46.57	244	-11	-10.3	-0.7	1
5358	1955-02-07	MONT LAURIER	QUE	7035160	-75.55	46.57	244	-5.5	-5.3	-0.2	1
5359	1955-02-11	MONT LAURIER	QUE	7035160	-75.55	46.57	244	-7.1	-6.9	-0.2	1
5360	1956-12-04	MONT LAURIER	QUE	7035160	-75.55	46.57	244	-12.6	-11.8	-0.8	1
5361	1957-08-26	MONT LAURIER	QUE	7035160	-75.55	46.57	244	14.8	15.6	-0.8	1
5362	1957-10-10	MONT LAURIER	QUE	7035160	-75.55	46.57	244	7.6	7.7	-0.1	1
5363	1957-10-18	MONT LAURIER	QUE	7035160	-75.55	46.57	244	8.2	12.8	-4.6	1
5364	1957-10-23	MONT LAURIER	QUE	7035160	-75.55	46.57	244	-0.3	9.6	-9.9	1
5365	1957-10-24	MONT LAURIER	QUE	7035160	-75.55	46.57	244	2	4.5	-2.5	1
5366	1957-12-07	MONT LAURIER	QUE	7035160	-75.55	46.57	244	-7.7	0.6	-8.3	1
5367	1957-12-11	MONT LAURIER	QUE	7035160	-75.55	46.57	244	-15.4	-12.9	-2.5	1
5368	1957-12-16	MONT LAURIER	QUE	7035160	-75.55	46.57	244	-8.8	-6.9	-1.9	1
5369	1957-12-21	MONT LAURIER	QUE	7035160	-75.55	46.57	244	0.9	7.7	-6.8	1
5370	1957-12-26	MONT LAURIER	QUE	7035160	-75.55	46.57	244	-3.1	-2.4	-0.7	1
5371	1957-12-29	MONT LAURIER	QUE	7035160	-75.55	46.57	244	-8.2	-3	-5.2	1

5372	1958-12-22	MONT LAURIER	QUE	7035160	-75.55	46.57	244	-11.6	-10.3	-1.3	1
5373	1958-12-26	MONT LAURIER	QUE	7035160	-75.55	46.57	244	-9.3	-8.8	-0.5	1
5374	1959-01-04	MONT LAURIER	QUE	7035160	-75.55	46.57	244	-11	-10.3	-0.7	1
5375	1959-01-15	MONT LAURIER	QUE	7035160	-75.55	46.57	244	-6	-5.3	-0.7	1
5376	1959-01-16	MONT LAURIER	QUE	7035160	-75.55	46.57	244	-17	-6.4	-10.6	1
5377	1959-01-22	MONT LAURIER	QUE	7035160	-75.55	46.57	244	-12.6	-3.5	-9.1	1
5378	1959-01-29	MONT LAURIER	QUE	7035160	-75.55	46.57	244	-19.8	-14.2	-5.6	1
5379	1959-04-06	MONT LAURIER	QUE	7035160	-75.55	46.57	244	2	2.2	-0.2	1
5380	1959-12-07	MONT LAURIER	QUE	7035160	-75.55	46.57	244	1.4	1.5	-0.1	1
5381	1959-12-20	MONT LAURIER	QUE	7035160	-75.55	46.57	244	-15.9	-6.9	-9	1
5382	1960-02-19	MONT LAURIER	QUE	7035160	-75.55	46.57	244	-7.7	-3	-4.7	1
5383	1960-02-25	MONT LAURIER	QUE	7035160	-75.55	46.57	244	-3.1	-2.4	-0.7	1
5384	1960-02-26	MONT LAURIER	QUE	7035160	-75.55	46.57	244	-7.1	-3	-4.1	1
5385	1960-12-26	MONT LAURIER	QUE	7035160	-75.55	46.57	244	-6.6	-6.4	-0.2	1
5386	1960-12-31	MONT LAURIER	QUE	7035160	-75.55	46.57	244	-15.4	-14.8	-0.6	1
5387	1962-11-11	MONT LAURIER	QUE	7035160	-75.55	46.57	244	0.9	1.5	-0.6	1
5388	1962-11-22	MONT LAURIER	QUE	7035160	-75.55	46.57	244	-0.8	0	-0.8	1
5389	1962-12-10	MONT LAURIER	QUE	7035160	-75.55	46.57	244	-3.7	-3.5	-0.2	1
5390	1962-12-26	MONT LAURIER	QUE	7035160	-75.55	46.57	244	-22.6	-7.3	-15.3	1
5391	1963-01-10	MONT LAURIER	QUE	7035160	-75.55	46.57	244	-4.9	-4.1	-0.8	1
5392	1963-01-20	MONT LAURIER	QUE	7035160	-75.55	46.57	244	-17.6	-17.1	-0.5	1
5393	1963-01-30	MONT LAURIER	QUE	7035160	-75.55	46.57	244	-11.6	-11.3	-0.3	1
5394	1963-08-29	MONT LAURIER	QUE	7035160	-75.55	46.57	244	13.7	13.9	-0.2	1
5395	1963-10-26	MONT LAURIER	QUE	7035160	-75.55	46.57	244	9.4	10.8	-1.4	1
5396	1964-12-25	MONT LAURIER	QUE	7035160	-75.55	46.57	244	-4.3	5	-9.3	1
5397	1964-12-26	MONT LAURIER	QUE	7035160	-75.55	46.57	244	-1.4	7.1	-8.5	1
5398	1964-12-28	MONT LAURIER	QUE	7035160	-75.55	46.57	244	-10.5	-9.3	-1.2	1
5399	1976-05-17	MONT LAURIER	QUE	7035160	-75.55	46.57	244	4.6	11.3	-6.7	1
5400	1978-12-29	MONT LAURIER	QUE	7035160	-75.55	46.57	244	-9.9	-5.3	-4.6	1
5401	1979-01-31	MONT LAURIER	QUE	7035160	-75.55	46.57	244	-10.5	-10.3	-0.2	1
5402	1995-03-19	MONT LAURIER	QUE	7035160	-75.55	46.57	244	3.2	4.1	-0.9	1
5403	1913-09-21	CHAPLEAU	ONT	6061361	-83.35	47.82	448	6.4	6.7	-0.3	1
5404	1913-12-24	CHAPLEAU	ONT	6061361	-83.35	47.82	448	-9.1	-6.1	-3	1
5405	1914-04-18	CHAPLEAU	ONT	6061361	-83.35	47.82	448	-3	2.8	-5.8	1

5406	1914-05-20	CHAPLEAU	ONT	6061361	-83.35	47.82	448	11.9	13.9	-2	1
5407	1916-11-23	CHAPLEAU	ONT	6061361	-83.35	47.82	448	-4.4	-3.9	-0.5	1
5408	1924-03-27	CHAPLEAU	ONT	6061361	-83.35	47.82	448	-5.7	-5.6	-0.1	1
5409	1925-03-21	CHAPLEAU	ONT	6061361	-83.35	47.82	448	-4.4	-2.2	-2.2	1
5410	1939-12-03	CHAPLEAU	ONT	6061361	-83.35	47.82	448	-8.1	-7.8	-0.3	1
5411	1939-12-13	CHAPLEAU	ONT	6061361	-83.35	47.82	448	-11.2	-11.1	-0.1	1
5412	1940-01-15	CHAPLEAU	ONT	6061361	-83.35	47.82	448	-11.2	-11.1	-0.1	1
5413	1947-01-19	CHAPLEAU	ONT	6061361	-83.35	47.82	448	-6.9	-6.7	-0.2	1
5414	1949-08-23	CHAPLEAU	ONT	6061361	-83.35	47.82	448	13.1	13.3	-0.2	1
5415	1949-09-13	CHAPLEAU	ONT	6061361	-83.35	47.82	448	10.1	10.6	-0.5	1
5416	1949-10-30	CHAPLEAU	ONT	6061361	-83.35	47.82	448	3.8	3.9	-0.1	1
5417	1950-02-28	CHAPLEAU	ONT	6061361	-83.35	47.82	448	-9.6	-9.4	-0.2	1
5418	1992-12-24	LANSDOWNE HOUSE	ONT	6014353	-87.88	52.23	253	-26.1	-24.8	-1.3	1
5419	1994-05-16	LANSDOWNE HOUSE	ONT	6014353	-87.88	52.23	253	11.3	11.4	-0.1	1
5420	1994-12-05	LANSDOWNE HOUSE	ONT	6014353	-87.88	52.23	253	-17.8	-13.7	-4.1	1
5421	1914-11-01	TADOUSSAC	QUE	7042840	-69.7	48.15	61	2.5	3.9	-1.4	1
5422	1914-11-02	TADOUSSAC	QUE	7042840	-69.7	48.15	61	2.5	2.8	-0.3	1
5423	1917-04-02	TADOUSSAC	QUE	7042840	-69.7	48.15	61	2.3	3.3	-1	1
5424	1917-04-11	TADOUSSAC	QUE	7042840	-69.7	48.15	61	2.5	4.4	-1.9	1
5425	1917-04-24	TADOUSSAC	QUE	7042840	-69.7	48.15	61	2.2	3.3	-1.1	1
5426	1917-05-02	TADOUSSAC	QUE	7042840	-69.7	48.15	61	3.1	3.3	-0.2	1
5427	1917-05-15	TADOUSSAC	QUE	7042840	-69.7	48.15	61	2.9	3.9	-1	1
5428	1917-05-21	TADOUSSAC	QUE	7042840	-69.7	48.15	61	11.5	12.8	-1.3	1
5429	1917-08-30	TADOUSSAC	QUE	7042840	-69.7	48.15	61	11.5	11.7	-0.2	1
5430	1917-09-11	TADOUSSAC	QUE	7042840	-69.7	48.15	61	12	13.3	-1.3	1
5431	1917-11-11	TADOUSSAC	QUE	7042840	-69.7	48.15	61	0.5	0.6	-0.1	1
5432	1917-12-21	TADOUSSAC	QUE	7042840	-69.7	48.15	61	2.5	3.3	-0.8	1
5433	1918-02-25	TADOUSSAC	QUE	7042840	-69.7	48.15	61	2.5	2.8	-0.3	1
5434	1918-03-30	TADOUSSAC	QUE	7042840	-69.7	48.15	61	2.5	3.3	-0.8	1
5435	1918-04-13	TADOUSSAC	QUE	7042840	-69.7	48.15	61	2.5	4.4	-1.9	1
5436	1918-05-06	TADOUSSAC	QUE	7042840	-69.7	48.15	61	2.6	2.8	-0.2	1
5437	1918-05-20	TADOUSSAC	QUE	7042840	-69.7	48.15	61	10.7	12.2	-1.5	1
5438	1918-05-21	TADOUSSAC	QUE	7042840	-69.7	48.15	61	10.6	11.1	-0.5	1
5439	1918-06-13	TADOUSSAC	QUE	7042840	-69.7	48.15	61	13.6	13.9	-0.3	1

5440	1918-06-14	TADOUSSAC	QUE	7042840	-69.7	48.15	61	13.6	13.9	-0.3	1
5441	1918-10-05	TADOUSSAC	QUE	7042840	-69.7	48.15	61	2.7	2.8	-0.1	1
5442	1918-10-06	TADOUSSAC	QUE	7042840	-69.7	48.15	61	2.6	2.8	-0.2	1
5443	1918-10-18	TADOUSSAC	QUE	7042840	-69.7	48.15	61	5.7	6.7	-1	1
5444	1918-11-20	TADOUSSAC	QUE	7042840	-69.7	48.15	61	0.7	1.1	-0.4	1
5445	1918-12-12	TADOUSSAC	QUE	7042840	-69.7	48.15	61	-6.3	-6.1	-0.2	1
5446	1918-12-20	TADOUSSAC	QUE	7042840	-69.7	48.15	61	1.2	1.7	-0.5	1
5447	1919-01-01	TADOUSSAC	QUE	7042840	-69.7	48.15	61	-1.4	-1.1	-0.3	1
5448	1919-03-16	TADOUSSAC	QUE	7042840	-69.7	48.15	61	1.2	1.7	-0.5	1
5449	1919-05-01	TADOUSSAC	QUE	7042840	-69.7	48.15	61	3.2	3.3	-0.1	1
5450	1919-05-02	TADOUSSAC	QUE	7042840	-69.7	48.15	61	3.5	3.9	-0.4	1
5451	1919-05-06	TADOUSSAC	QUE	7042840	-69.7	48.15	61	4.6	5.6	-1	1
5452	1919-05-23	TADOUSSAC	QUE	7042840	-69.7	48.15	61	12.3	13.3	-1	1
5453	1919-07-03	TADOUSSAC	QUE	7042840	-69.7	48.15	61	13.4	13.9	-0.5	1
5454	1919-07-12	TADOUSSAC	QUE	7042840	-69.7	48.15	61	17.6	18.3	-0.7	1
5455	1920-03-04	TADOUSSAC	QUE	7042840	-69.7	48.15	61	2.2	2.8	-0.6	1
5456	1920-05-26	TADOUSSAC	QUE	7042840	-69.7	48.15	61	20.2	20.6	-0.4	1
5457	1920-09-22	TADOUSSAC	QUE	7042840	-69.7	48.15	61	18.7	18.9	-0.2	1
5458	1920-11-10	TADOUSSAC	QUE	7042840	-69.7	48.15	61	2.7	2.8	-0.1	1
5459	1921-02-28	TADOUSSAC	QUE	7042840	-69.7	48.15	61	-2.9	-2.8	-0.1	1
5460	1921-03-09	TADOUSSAC	QUE	7042840	-69.7	48.15	61	2.7	3.3	-0.6	1
5461	1922-06-25	TADOUSSAC	QUE	7042840	-69.7	48.15	61	19.3	20	-0.7	1
5462	1922-10-23	TADOUSSAC	QUE	7042840	-69.7	48.15	61	6.9	7.2	-0.3	1
5463	1923-03-02	TADOUSSAC	QUE	7042840	-69.7	48.15	61	-6.8	-6.7	-0.1	1
5464	1923-10-08	TADOUSSAC	QUE	7042840	-69.7	48.15	61	4.1	4.4	-0.3	1
5465	1925-10-18	TADOUSSAC	QUE	7042840	-69.7	48.15	61	2.7	2.8	-0.1	1
5466	1926-06-19	TADOUSSAC	QUE	7042840	-69.7	48.15	61	14.7	15	-0.3	1
5467	1930-09-15	TADOUSSAC	QUE	7042840	-69.7	48.15	61	6.3	6.7	-0.4	1
5468	1930-11-17	TADOUSSAC	QUE	7042840	-69.7	48.15	61	3.5	3.9	-0.4	1
5469	1931-10-30	TADOUSSAC	QUE	7042840	-69.7	48.15	61	2.7	2.8	-0.1	1
5470	1932-07-08	TADOUSSAC	QUE	7042840	-69.7	48.15	61	14	14.4	-0.4	1
5471	1934-09-17	TADOUSSAC	QUE	7042840	-69.7	48.15	61	14.6	15	-0.4	1
5472	1935-05-10	TADOUSSAC	QUE	7042840	-69.7	48.15	61	8.8	8.9	-0.1	1
5473	1936-10-07	TADOUSSAC	QUE	7042840	-69.7	48.15	61	6.2	6.7	-0.5	1

5474	1937-04-23	TADOUSSAC	QUE	7042840	-69.7	48.15	61	5.1	5.6	-0.5	1
5475	1937-11-29	TADOUSSAC	QUE	7042840	-69.7	48.15	61	3.5	3.9	-0.4	1
5476	1938-11-09	TADOUSSAC	QUE	7042840	-69.7	48.15	61	4	4.4	-0.4	1
5477	1939-09-30	TADOUSSAC	QUE	7042840	-69.7	48.15	61	8.2	8.3	-0.1	1
5478	1940-11-21	TADOUSSAC	QUE	7042840	-69.7	48.15	61	3.6	3.9	-0.3	1
5479	1942-09-20	TADOUSSAC	QUE	7042840	-69.7	48.15	61	14	14.4	-0.4	1
5480	1942-11-28	TADOUSSAC	QUE	7042840	-69.7	48.15	61	-6.3	-6.1	-0.2	1
5481	1943-05-27	TADOUSSAC	QUE	7042840	-69.7	48.15	61	11.4	11.7	-0.3	1
5482	1943-08-10	TADOUSSAC	QUE	7042840	-69.7	48.15	61	16.5	16.7	-0.2	1
5483	1943-10-09	TADOUSSAC	QUE	7042840	-69.7	48.15	61	14	14.4	-0.4	1
5484	1943-10-23	TADOUSSAC	QUE	7042840	-69.7	48.15	61	3.2	3.3	-0.1	1
5485	1943-10-31	TADOUSSAC	QUE	7042840	-69.7	48.15	61	5.1	5.6	-0.5	1
5486	1943-11-08	TADOUSSAC	QUE	7042840	-69.7	48.15	61	2.7	2.8	-0.1	1
5487	1944-06-08	TADOUSSAC	QUE	7042840	-69.7	48.15	61	16	16.1	-0.1	1
5488	1944-07-10	TADOUSSAC	QUE	7042840	-69.7	48.15	61	16.5	16.7	-0.2	1
5489	1944-10-14	TADOUSSAC	QUE	7042840	-69.7	48.15	61	4.6	5	-0.4	1
5490	1945-05-15	TADOUSSAC	QUE	7042840	-69.7	48.15	61	5.1	5.6	-0.5	1
5491	1947-03-06	TADOUSSAC	QUE	7042840	-69.7	48.15	61	3.2	3.3	-0.1	1
5492	1948-11-11	TADOUSSAC	QUE	7042840	-69.7	48.15	61	5.7	6.1	-0.4	1
5493	1951-12-19	TADOUSSAC	QUE	7042840	-69.7	48.15	61	-22.1	-21.7	-0.4	1
5494	1957-02-18	TADOUSSAC	QUE	7042840	-69.7	48.15	61	-5.8	-5.6	-0.2	1
5495	1958-12-10	TADOUSSAC	QUE	7042840	-69.7	48.15	61	-19.8	-18.3	-1.5	1
5496	1959-05-14	TADOUSSAC	QUE	7042840	-69.7	48.15	61	6.8	7.2	-0.4	1
5497	1982-02-23	TADOUSSAC	QUE	7042840	-69.7	48.15	61	-10	-9	-1	1
5498	1982-11-19	TADOUSSAC	QUE	7042840	-69.7	48.15	61	1	2	-1	1
5499	1982-11-27	TADOUSSAC	QUE	7042840	-69.7	48.15	61	-8	-6	-2	1
5500	2009-03-05	DARFIELD	BC	1162265	-120.18	51.3	466	-5	-4	-1	1
5501	2010-11-18	DARFIELD	BC	1162265	-120.18	51.3	466	-7.5	-6.5	-1	1
5502	2014-01-03	DARFIELD	BC	1162265	-120.18	51.3	466	-1.5	-1	-0.5	1
5503	2014-12-29	DARFIELD	BC	1162265	-120.18	51.3	466	-7	-3	-4	1
5504	2013-04-05	ENTRANCE	ALTA	306A009	-117.7	53.37	1011	-5.6	-5.2	-0.4	1
5505	1914-04-06	ROBERVAL	QUE	7066686	-72.27	48.52	179	-1.2	-1.1	-0.1	1
5506	1914-11-10	ROBERVAL	QUE	7066686	-72.27	48.52	179	-12.6	-11.7	-0.9	1
5507	1914-12-25	ROBERVAL	QUE	7066686	-72.27	48.52	179	-34.3	-32.2	-2.1	1

5508	1915-01-13	ROBERVAL	QUE	7066686	-72.27	48.52	179	-13.9	-12.2	-1.7	1
5509	1915-01-22	ROBERVAL	QUE	7066686	-72.27	48.52	179	-23.8	-22.2	-1.6	1
5510	1916-01-03	ROBERVAL	QUE	7066686	-72.27	48.52	179	-15.2	-13.3	-1.9	1
5511	1916-02-06	ROBERVAL	QUE	7066686	-72.27	48.52	179	-15.9	-15	-0.9	1
5512	1916-09-23	ROBERVAL	QUE	7066686	-72.27	48.52	179	10	10.6	-0.6	1
5513	1916-11-18	ROBERVAL	QUE	7066686	-72.27	48.52	179	-8.4	-7.2	-1.2	1
5514	1916-11-23	ROBERVAL	QUE	7066686	-72.27	48.52	179	-1	-0.6	-0.4	1
5515	1916-12-11	ROBERVAL	QUE	7066686	-72.27	48.52	179	-12.6	-12.2	-0.4	1
5516	1916-12-16	ROBERVAL	QUE	7066686	-72.27	48.52	179	-15.9	-15	-0.9	1
5517	1916-12-17	ROBERVAL	QUE	7066686	-72.27	48.52	179	-15.9	-15.6	-0.3	1
5518	1916-12-18	ROBERVAL	QUE	7066686	-72.27	48.52	179	-15.9	-14.4	-1.5	1
5519	1917-01-23	ROBERVAL	QUE	7066686	-72.27	48.52	179	-27.1	-23.9	-3.2	1
5520	1917-06-08	ROBERVAL	QUE	7066686	-72.27	48.52	179	9.7	10.6	-0.9	1
5521	1917-06-11	ROBERVAL	QUE	7066686	-72.27	48.52	179	10.1	11.1	-1	1
5522	1917-06-15	ROBERVAL	QUE	7066686	-72.27	48.52	179	19.9	20	-0.1	1
5523	1918-01-05	ROBERVAL	QUE	7066686	-72.27	48.52	179	-15.9	-15	-0.9	1
5524	1918-01-09	ROBERVAL	QUE	7066686	-72.27	48.52	179	-13.3	-12.8	-0.5	1
5525	1918-05-12	ROBERVAL	QUE	7066686	-72.27	48.52	179	3.7	3.9	-0.2	1
5526	1918-12-24	ROBERVAL	QUE	7066686	-72.27	48.52	179	-18.1	-16.7	-1.4	1
5527	1919-03-28	ROBERVAL	QUE	7066686	-72.27	48.52	179	-13.3	-12.8	-0.5	1
5528	1919-11-16	ROBERVAL	QUE	7066686	-72.27	48.52	179	-3.4	-3.3	-0.1	1
5529	1921-10-19	ROBERVAL	QUE	7066686	-72.27	48.52	179	6.4	7.2	-0.8	1
5530	1921-12-20	ROBERVAL	QUE	7066686	-72.27	48.52	179	-20.4	-17.2	-3.2	1
5531	1922-01-18	ROBERVAL	QUE	7066686	-72.27	48.52	179	-17.5	-17.2	-0.3	1
5532	1922-03-11	ROBERVAL	QUE	7066686	-72.27	48.52	179	-4.9	-2.8	-2.1	1
5533	1922-09-10	ROBERVAL	QUE	7066686	-72.27	48.52	179	12.2	15	-2.8	1
5534	1922-11-20	ROBERVAL	QUE	7066686	-72.27	48.52	179	-3.9	-2.8	-1.1	1
5535	1922-12-03	ROBERVAL	QUE	7066686	-72.27	48.52	179	-15.9	-12.8	-3.1	1
5536	1922-12-05	ROBERVAL	QUE	7066686	-72.27	48.52	179	-18.1	-16.1	-2	1
5537	1922-12-16	ROBERVAL	QUE	7066686	-72.27	48.52	179	-15.2	-13.3	-1.9	1
5538	1922-12-17	ROBERVAL	QUE	7066686	-72.27	48.52	179	-18.1	-14.4	-3.7	1
5539	1923-08-11	ROBERVAL	QUE	7066686	-72.27	48.52	179	9.6	11.1	-1.5	1
5540	1923-10-29	ROBERVAL	QUE	7066686	-72.27	48.52	179	-3.9	1.7	-5.6	1
5541	1923-11-07	ROBERVAL	QUE	7066686	-72.27	48.52	179	-4.9	-4.4	-0.5	1

5542	1923-12-27	ROBERVAL	QUE	7066686	-72.27	48.52	179	-13.9	-11.7	-2.2	1
5543	1924-03-05	ROBERVAL	QUE	7066686	-72.27	48.52	179	-2.1	-1.1	-1	1
5544	1924-07-29	ROBERVAL	QUE	7066686	-72.27	48.52	179	16.4	17.2	-0.8	1
5545	1924-09-02	ROBERVAL	QUE	7066686	-72.27	48.52	179	15.1	15.6	-0.5	1
5546	1924-09-16	ROBERVAL	QUE	7066686	-72.27	48.52	179	13.4	14.4	-1	1
5547	1924-11-29	ROBERVAL	QUE	7066686	-72.27	48.52	179	-7.1	-6.7	-0.4	1
5548	1924-12-11	ROBERVAL	QUE	7066686	-72.27	48.52	179	-18.1	-16.7	-1.4	1
5549	1924-12-15	ROBERVAL	QUE	7066686	-72.27	48.52	179	-22.1	-20.6	-1.5	1
5550	1924-12-19	ROBERVAL	QUE	7066686	-72.27	48.52	179	-23.2	-21.7	-1.5	1
5551	1924-12-25	ROBERVAL	QUE	7066686	-72.27	48.52	179	-16.4	-15	-1.4	1
5552	1924-12-26	ROBERVAL	QUE	7066686	-72.27	48.52	179	-32.1	-31.7	-0.4	1
5553	1924-12-31	ROBERVAL	QUE	7066686	-72.27	48.52	179	-25.4	-23.3	-2.1	1
5554	1925-01-06	ROBERVAL	QUE	7066686	-72.27	48.52	179	-18.1	-17.8	-0.3	1
5555	1925-02-01	ROBERVAL	QUE	7066686	-72.27	48.52	179	-21	-20	-1	1
5556	1925-08-20	ROBERVAL	QUE	7066686	-72.27	48.52	179	15.8	16.7	-0.9	1
5557	1925-11-23	ROBERVAL	QUE	7066686	-72.27	48.52	179	-11.7	-11.1	-0.6	1
5558	1925-11-24	ROBERVAL	QUE	7066686	-72.27	48.52	179	-11.7	-10.6	-1.1	1
5559	1925-11-25	ROBERVAL	QUE	7066686	-72.27	48.52	179	-11.7	-11.1	-0.6	1
5560	1925-11-27	ROBERVAL	QUE	7066686	-72.27	48.52	179	-12.6	-12.2	-0.4	1
5561	1925-11-28	ROBERVAL	QUE	7066686	-72.27	48.52	179	-21.5	-20.6	-0.9	1
5562	1925-11-29	ROBERVAL	QUE	7066686	-72.27	48.52	179	-21	-20	-1	1
5563	1926-02-14	ROBERVAL	QUE	7066686	-72.27	48.52	179	-14.6	-13.3	-1.3	1
5564	1926-02-15	ROBERVAL	QUE	7066686	-72.27	48.52	179	-8.4	-7.8	-0.6	1
5565	1926-04-09	ROBERVAL	QUE	7066686	-72.27	48.52	179	-11.1	-9.4	-1.7	1
5566	1931-02-13	ROBERVAL	QUE	7066686	-72.27	48.52	179	-14.7	-11.1	-3.6	1
5567	1931-03-29	ROBERVAL	QUE	7066686	-72.27	48.52	179	-1.3	0	-1.3	1
5568	1932-02-23	ROBERVAL	QUE	7066686	-72.27	48.52	179	-24.9	-24.4	-0.5	1
5569	1933-01-16	ROBERVAL	QUE	7066686	-72.27	48.52	179	-13.9	-13.3	-0.6	1
5570	1933-01-29	ROBERVAL	QUE	7066686	-72.27	48.52	179	-7.1	-6.1	-1	1
5571	1933-02-04	ROBERVAL	QUE	7066686	-72.27	48.52	179	-15.2	-14.4	-0.8	1
5572	1933-07-01	ROBERVAL	QUE	7066686	-72.27	48.52	179	12.2	13.9	-1.7	1
5573	1933-09-09	ROBERVAL	QUE	7066686	-72.27	48.52	179	12.8	13.3	-0.5	1
5574	1933-11-23	ROBERVAL	QUE	7066686	-72.27	48.52	179	-14.6	-12.8	-1.8	1
5575	1933-11-26	ROBERVAL	QUE	7066686	-72.27	48.52	179	-16.4	-16.1	-0.3	1

5576	1933-12-02	ROBERVAL	QUE	7066686	-72.27	48.52	179	-18.8	-17.8	-1	1
5577	1933-12-15	ROBERVAL	QUE	7066686	-72.27	48.52	179	-31	-28.9	-2.1	1
5578	1934-08-10	ROBERVAL	QUE	7066686	-72.27	48.52	179	17.7	20	-2.3	1
5579	1934-09-01	ROBERVAL	QUE	7066686	-72.27	48.52	179	13.6	14.4	-0.8	1
5580	1934-10-23	ROBERVAL	QUE	7066686	-72.27	48.52	179	8.8	8.9	-0.1	1
5581	1936-06-12	ROBERVAL	QUE	7066686	-72.27	48.52	179	14.5	15	-0.5	1
5582	1936-07-04	ROBERVAL	QUE	7066686	-72.27	48.52	179	13.6	15.6	-2	1
5583	1936-07-25	ROBERVAL	QUE	7066686	-72.27	48.52	179	14	15	-1	1
5584	1936-08-29	ROBERVAL	QUE	7066686	-72.27	48.52	179	13.3	14.4	-1.1	1
5585	1936-09-01	ROBERVAL	QUE	7066686	-72.27	48.52	179	12.8	13.3	-0.5	1
5586	1939-12-24	ROBERVAL	QUE	7066686	-72.27	48.52	179	-16.1	-15	-1.1	1
5587	1940-01-28	ROBERVAL	QUE	7066686	-72.27	48.52	179	-12.6	-11.7	-0.9	1
5588	1941-12-28	ROBERVAL	QUE	7066686	-72.27	48.52	179	-13.2	-12.8	-0.4	1
5589	1944-06-16	ROBERVAL	QUE	7066686	-72.27	48.52	179	15.1	15.6	-0.5	1
5590	1944-07-20	ROBERVAL	QUE	7066686	-72.27	48.52	179	15.9	16.1	-0.2	1
5591	1944-09-21	ROBERVAL	QUE	7066686	-72.27	48.52	179	11.9	12.2	-0.3	1
5592	1944-10-10	ROBERVAL	QUE	7066686	-72.27	48.52	179	4.1	4.4	-0.3	1
5593	1944-11-25	ROBERVAL	QUE	7066686	-72.27	48.52	179	-0.1	0	-0.1	1
5594	1947-11-14	ROBERVAL	QUE	7066686	-72.27	48.52	179	-2.9	-2.8	-0.1	1
5595	1948-12-18	ROBERVAL	QUE	7066686	-72.27	48.52	179	-9.1	-8.9	-0.2	1
5596	1948-12-28	ROBERVAL	QUE	7066686	-72.27	48.52	179	-18.3	-17.8	-0.5	1
5597	1949-01-24	ROBERVAL	QUE	7066686	-72.27	48.52	179	-24.9	-23.3	-1.6	1
5598	1950-12-06	ROBERVAL	QUE	7066686	-72.27	48.52	179	-9.6	-9.4	-0.2	1
5599	1950-12-17	ROBERVAL	QUE	7066686	-72.27	48.52	179	-13.9	-13.3	-0.6	1
5600	1952-11-23	ROBERVAL	QUE	7066686	-72.27	48.52	179	1.9	2.2	-0.3	1
5601	1979-11-10	ROBERVAL	QUE	7066686	-72.27	48.52	179	-2.3	-1.2	-1.1	1
5602	1979-11-29	ROBERVAL	QUE	7066686	-72.27	48.52	179	-5.3	-4.5	-0.8	1
5603	1987-05-28	ROBERVAL	QUE	7066686	-72.27	48.52	179	0	16.1	-16.1	1
5604	1989-07-07	ROBERVAL	QUE	7066686	-72.27	48.52	179	11	11.8	-0.8	1
5605	2003-03-12	ROBERVAL	QUE	7066686	-72.27	48.52	179	-20.5	-13.9	-6.6	1
5606	1985-09-26	LONGSTAFF BLUFF	NU	2402684	-75.13	68.9	161	0.5	1.4	-0.9	1
5607	1994-11-28	LONGSTAFF BLUFF	NU	2402684	-75.13	68.9	161	-31.9	-30.2	-1.7	1
5608	1999-05-27	LONGSTAFF BLUFF	NU	2402684	-75.13	68.9	161	-4.7	-1.4	-3.3	1
5609	1999-10-17	LONGSTAFF BLUFF	NU	2402684	-75.13	68.9	161	-12.6	-8.5	-4.1	1

5610	2010-04-20	BROUGHTON	NU	2400570	-63.78	67.53	584	-11.9	-11.2	-0.7	1
5611	2010-04-21	BROUGHTON	NU	2400570	-63.78	67.53	584	-11.4	-10.4	-1	1
5612	2010-04-25	BROUGHTON	NU	2400570	-63.78	67.53	584	-8.4	-8.2	-0.2	1
5613	1878-12-04	OWEN SOUND	ONT	6116132	-80.93	44.58	179	-3.3	-3.1	-0.2	1
5614	1878-12-23	OWEN SOUND	ONT	6116132	-80.93	44.58	179	-9.4	-9	-0.4	1
5615	1879-03-30	OWEN SOUND	ONT	6116132	-80.93	44.58	179	-1.7	-1.6	-0.1	1
5616	1879-04-30	OWEN SOUND	ONT	6116132	-80.93	44.58	179	1.7	2.1	-0.4	1
5617	1880-01-20	OWEN SOUND	ONT	6116132	-80.93	44.58	179	-4.4	-4.3	-0.1	1
5618	1880-12-15	OWEN SOUND	ONT	6116132	-80.93	44.58	179	-3.3	-3.1	-0.2	1
5619	1881-02-28	OWEN SOUND	ONT	6116132	-80.93	44.58	179	-8.3	-8	-0.3	1
5620	1881-12-07	OWEN SOUND	ONT	6116132	-80.93	44.58	179	-1.1	-0.2	-0.9	1
5621	1882-11-13	OWEN SOUND	ONT	6116132	-80.93	44.58	179	0.6	1.1	-0.5	1
5622	1882-12-07	OWEN SOUND	ONT	6116132	-80.93	44.58	179	-11.1	-10.7	-0.4	1
5623	1883-01-04	OWEN SOUND	ONT	6116132	-80.93	44.58	179	-11.1	-10.7	-0.4	1
5624	1883-11-30	OWEN SOUND	ONT	6116132	-80.93	44.58	179	-6.7	-5.5	-1.2	1
5625	1883-12-14	OWEN SOUND	ONT	6116132	-80.93	44.58	179	-0.6	-0.3	-0.3	1
5626	1884-01-14	OWEN SOUND	ONT	6116132	-80.93	44.58	179	-7.8	-7.3	-0.5	1
5627	1885-01-26	OWEN SOUND	ONT	6116132	-80.93	44.58	179	-15.6	-15.4	-0.2	1
5628	1885-12-31	OWEN SOUND	ONT	6116132	-80.93	44.58	179	1.1	1.6	-0.5	1
5629	1886-01-08	OWEN SOUND	ONT	6116132	-80.93	44.58	179	-16.7	-15.9	-0.8	1
5630	1886-10-25	OWEN SOUND	ONT	6116132	-80.93	44.58	179	1.1	1.6	-0.5	1
5631	1887-04-12	OWEN SOUND	ONT	6116132	-80.93	44.58	179	-0.6	-0.2	-0.4	1
5632	1887-10-21	OWEN SOUND	ONT	6116132	-80.93	44.58	179	2.2	2.6	-0.4	1
5633	1887-11-30	OWEN SOUND	ONT	6116132	-80.93	44.58	179	-11.1	-10.8	-0.3	1
5634	1888-03-03	OWEN SOUND	ONT	6116132	-80.93	44.58	179	-12.2	-11.8	-0.4	1
5635	2007-10-09	OWEN SOUND	ONT	6116132	-80.93	44.58	179	7.5	18	-10.5	1
5636	2007-03-21	BAY D'ESPOIR	NFLD	8400413	-55.8	47.98	23	-5	-1	-4	1
5637	2014-11-08	BAY D'ESPOIR	NFLD	8400413	-55.8	47.98	23	3	7	-4	1
5638	2016-09-15	BAY D'ESPOIR	NFLD	8400413	-55.8	47.98	23	10	12	-2	1
5639	2010-03-25	FORT RELIANCE	NWT	2201903	-109.17	62.72	168	-14.6	-12	-2.6	1
5640	2010-03-26	FORT RELIANCE	NWT	2201903	-109.17	62.72	168	-19.3	-8.3	-11	1
5641	2007-08-22	COLLINS BAY	SASK	4061632	-103.7	58.18	490	10	12	-2	1
5642	2007-11-23	COLLINS BAY	SASK	4061632	-103.7	58.18	490	-21	-20	-1	1
5643	2008-03-03	COLLINS BAY	SASK	4061632	-103.7	58.18	490	-24	-18	-6	1

5644	2008-03-11	COLLINS BAY	SASK	4061632	-103.7	58.18	490	-18	-12.5	-5.5	1
5645	2008-09-23	COLLINS BAY	SASK	4061632	-103.7	58.18	490	5	7	-2	1
5646	2008-12-07	COLLINS BAY	SASK	4061632	-103.7	58.18	490	-30	-25	-5	1
5647	2009-01-21	COLLINS BAY	SASK	4061632	-103.7	58.18	490	-25	-22	-3	1
5648	2009-02-12	COLLINS BAY	SASK	4061632	-103.7	58.18	490	-18	-17	-1	1
5649	2009-04-07	COLLINS BAY	SASK	4061632	-103.7	58.18	490	-6	-3	-3	1
5650	1917-01-01	ATIKOKAN	ONT	6020LPQ	-91.58	48.8	389	-21	-20.7	-0.3	1
5651	1917-01-02	ATIKOKAN	ONT	6020LPQ	-91.58	48.8	389	-21	-20.4	-0.6	1
5652	1917-04-18	ATIKOKAN	ONT	6020LPQ	-91.58	48.8	389	4.5	5.1	-0.6	1
5653	1917-04-19	ATIKOKAN	ONT	6020LPQ	-91.58	48.8	389	4.5	5.6	-1.1	1
5654	1917-12-01	ATIKOKAN	ONT	6020LPQ	-91.58	48.8	389	-10.5	-9.4	-1.1	1
5655	1918-09-01	ATIKOKAN	ONT	6020LPQ	-91.58	48.8	389	17.9	18.1	-0.2	1
5656	1918-09-04	ATIKOKAN	ONT	6020LPQ	-91.58	48.8	389	11.9	12.2	-0.3	1
5657	1918-09-08	ATIKOKAN	ONT	6020LPQ	-91.58	48.8	389	21.7	22	-0.3	1
5658	1918-09-19	ATIKOKAN	ONT	6020LPQ	-91.58	48.8	389	7.6	8.8	-1.2	1
5659	1918-09-20	ATIKOKAN	ONT	6020LPQ	-91.58	48.8	389	9.6	10.1	-0.5	1
5660	1918-09-22	ATIKOKAN	ONT	6020LPQ	-91.58	48.8	389	17.2	18.1	-0.9	1
5661	1918-09-29	ATIKOKAN	ONT	6020LPQ	-91.58	48.8	389	7.6	7.7	-0.1	1
5662	1918-09-30	ATIKOKAN	ONT	6020LPQ	-91.58	48.8	389	8.1	8.8	-0.7	1
5663	1918-10-01	ATIKOKAN	ONT	6020LPQ	-91.58	48.8	389	10.2	10.9	-0.7	1
5664	1918-10-07	ATIKOKAN	ONT	6020LPQ	-91.58	48.8	389	8.1	10.5	-2.4	1
5665	1918-10-14	ATIKOKAN	ONT	6020LPQ	-91.58	48.8	389	5.7	7.7	-2	1
5666	1918-10-17	ATIKOKAN	ONT	6020LPQ	-91.58	48.8	389	9.1	10.1	-1	1
5667	1918-10-19	ATIKOKAN	ONT	6020LPQ	-91.58	48.8	389	7.6	10.1	-2.5	1
5668	1918-10-23	ATIKOKAN	ONT	6020LPQ	-91.58	48.8	389	5.7	6.2	-0.5	1
5669	1918-10-26	ATIKOKAN	ONT	6020LPQ	-91.58	48.8	389	0.1	2.1	-2	1
5670	1918-10-27	ATIKOKAN	ONT	6020LPQ	-91.58	48.8	389	2	5.1	-3.1	1
5671	1918-10-29	ATIKOKAN	ONT	6020LPQ	-91.58	48.8	389	2.7	5	-2.3	1
5672	1918-10-30	ATIKOKAN	ONT	6020LPQ	-91.58	48.8	389	-0.5	0.2	-0.7	1
5673	1918-10-31	ATIKOKAN	ONT	6020LPQ	-91.58	48.8	389	-3.1	-1.3	-1.8	1
5674	1918-11-04	ATIKOKAN	ONT	6020LPQ	-91.58	48.8	389	3.9	5.1	-1.2	1
5675	1918-11-05	ATIKOKAN	ONT	6020LPQ	-91.58	48.8	389	8.6	10.9	-2.3	1
5676	1918-11-07	ATIKOKAN	ONT	6020LPQ	-91.58	48.8	389	6.7	7.3	-0.6	1
5677	1918-11-09	ATIKOKAN	ONT	6020LPQ	-91.58	48.8	389	0.1	0.2	-0.1	1

5678	1918-11-10	ATIKOKAN	ONT	6020LPQ	-91.58	48.8	389	-2.6	-0.2	-2.4	1
5679	1918-11-16	ATIKOKAN	ONT	6020LPQ	-91.58	48.8	389	9.6	10.1	-0.5	1
5680	1918-11-17	ATIKOKAN	ONT	6020LPQ	-91.58	48.8	389	8.6	10.1	-1.5	1
5681	1918-11-20	ATIKOKAN	ONT	6020LPQ	-91.58	48.8	389	-2.6	0.7	-3.3	1
5682	1918-11-23	ATIKOKAN	ONT	6020LPQ	-91.58	48.8	389	-0.5	-0.2	-0.3	1
5683	1918-12-18	ATIKOKAN	ONT	6020LPQ	-91.58	48.8	389	-1.3	-0.2	-1.1	1
5684	1918-12-19	ATIKOKAN	ONT	6020LPQ	-91.58	48.8	389	1.5	2.9	-1.4	1
5685	1918-12-21	ATIKOKAN	ONT	6020LPQ	-91.58	48.8	389	-0.6	0.2	-0.8	1
5686	1918-12-26	ATIKOKAN	ONT	6020LPQ	-91.58	48.8	389	-6.5	-6.1	-0.4	1
5687	1918-12-27	ATIKOKAN	ONT	6020LPQ	-91.58	48.8	389	-10.1	-9.9	-0.2	1
5688	1919-02-11	ATIKOKAN	ONT	6020LPQ	-91.58	48.8	389	-1.9	-1.3	-0.6	1
5689	1919-02-12	ATIKOKAN	ONT	6020LPQ	-91.58	48.8	389	-1.4	-1.3	-0.1	1
5690	1919-02-13	ATIKOKAN	ONT	6020LPQ	-91.58	48.8	389	-3.1	-3	-0.1	1
5691	1919-03-25	ATIKOKAN	ONT	6020LPQ	-91.58	48.8	389	5.7	6.3	-0.6	1
5692	1919-03-29	ATIKOKAN	ONT	6020LPQ	-91.58	48.8	389	-0.6	0.2	-0.8	1
5693	1919-10-14	ATIKOKAN	ONT	6020LPQ	-91.58	48.8	389	3.9	4.3	-0.4	1
5694	1919-10-24	ATIKOKAN	ONT	6020LPQ	-91.58	48.8	389	-7.8	-6.1	-1.7	1
5695	1919-11-03	ATIKOKAN	ONT	6020LPQ	-91.58	48.8	389	-10.1	-9.9	-0.2	1
5696	1919-11-09	ATIKOKAN	ONT	6020LPQ	-91.58	48.8	389	1.5	3.7	-2.2	1
5697	1919-12-22	ATIKOKAN	ONT	6020LPQ	-91.58	48.8	389	-2.6	-0.7	-1.9	1
5698	1919-12-29	ATIKOKAN	ONT	6020LPQ	-91.58	48.8	389	-6.5	-5.5	-1	1
5699	1920-02-07	ATIKOKAN	ONT	6020LPQ	-91.58	48.8	389	-3.1	-2	-1.1	1
5700	1920-05-31	ATIKOKAN	ONT	6020LPQ	-91.58	48.8	389	10.7	12.2	-1.5	1
5701	1920-10-26	ATIKOKAN	ONT	6020LPQ	-91.58	48.8	389	8.6	9.6	-1	1
5702	1920-11-27	ATIKOKAN	ONT	6020LPQ	-91.58	48.8	389	0.1	1.3	-1.2	1
5703	1920-11-29	ATIKOKAN	ONT	6020LPQ	-91.58	48.8	389	-0.7	0.3	-1	1
5704	1920-12-03	ATIKOKAN	ONT	6020LPQ	-91.58	48.8	389	0.7	1.3	-0.6	1
5705	1923-09-12	ATIKOKAN	ONT	6020LPQ	-91.58	48.8	389	0.6	3.7	-3.1	1
5706	1923-09-13	ATIKOKAN	ONT	6020LPQ	-91.58	48.8	389	0.1	0.7	-0.6	1
5707	1923-09-28	ATIKOKAN	ONT	6020LPQ	-91.58	48.8	389	8.6	8.8	-0.2	1
5708	1923-09-29	ATIKOKAN	ONT	6020LPQ	-91.58	48.8	389	4.4	5.6	-1.2	1
5709	1923-10-12	ATIKOKAN	ONT	6020LPQ	-91.58	48.8	389	5.7	7.8	-2.1	1
5710	1923-10-13	ATIKOKAN	ONT	6020LPQ	-91.58	48.8	389	0.6	2.8	-2.2	1
5711	1923-10-24	ATIKOKAN	ONT	6020LPQ	-91.58	48.8	389	0.7	1.3	-0.6	1

5712	1923-10-25	ATIKOKAN	ONT	6020LPQ	-91.58	48.8	389	-1.4	1.3	-2.7	1
5713	1923-10-27	ATIKOKAN	ONT	6020LPQ	-91.58	48.8	389	-2	0.3	-2.3	1
5714	1923-10-28	ATIKOKAN	ONT	6020LPQ	-91.58	48.8	389	-2	-1.4	-0.6	1
5715	1923-10-29	ATIKOKAN	ONT	6020LPQ	-91.58	48.8	389	-8.9	-7.7	-1.2	1
5716	1923-11-03	ATIKOKAN	ONT	6020LPQ	-91.58	48.8	389	4.4	5.1	-0.7	1
5717	1923-11-10	ATIKOKAN	ONT	6020LPQ	-91.58	48.8	389	-0.6	-0.3	-0.3	1
5718	1923-11-11	ATIKOKAN	ONT	6020LPQ	-91.58	48.8	389	-7.8	-5.5	-2.3	1
5719	1923-11-16	ATIKOKAN	ONT	6020LPQ	-91.58	48.8	389	-2	-0.7	-1.3	1
5720	1923-11-20	ATIKOKAN	ONT	6020LPQ	-91.58	48.8	389	2.7	4.4	-1.7	1
5721	1923-11-23	ATIKOKAN	ONT	6020LPQ	-91.58	48.8	389	-9	-8.5	-0.5	1
5722	1923-11-25	ATIKOKAN	ONT	6020LPQ	-91.58	48.8	389	1.5	2.8	-1.3	1
5723	1923-12-08	ATIKOKAN	ONT	6020LPQ	-91.58	48.8	389	-5.3	-1.9	-3.4	1
5724	1923-12-26	ATIKOKAN	ONT	6020LPQ	-91.58	48.8	389	-15.1	-13.9	-1.2	1
5725	1923-12-28	ATIKOKAN	ONT	6020LPQ	-91.58	48.8	389	-15.2	-14.4	-0.8	1
5726	1924-01-09	ATIKOKAN	ONT	6020LPQ	-91.58	48.8	389	-19.5	-18.6	-0.9	1
5727	1924-01-15	ATIKOKAN	ONT	6020LPQ	-91.58	48.8	389	-15.2	-13.9	-1.3	1
5728	1924-01-19	ATIKOKAN	ONT	6020LPQ	-91.58	48.8	389	-22.1	-21.6	-0.5	1
5729	1924-01-24	ATIKOKAN	ONT	6020LPQ	-91.58	48.8	389	-17.5	-17.1	-0.4	1
5730	1924-01-30	ATIKOKAN	ONT	6020LPQ	-91.58	48.8	389	-7.7	-5.5	-2.2	1
5731	1924-02-01	ATIKOKAN	ONT	6020LPQ	-91.58	48.8	389	-6.6	-5.5	-1.1	1
5732	1924-02-09	ATIKOKAN	ONT	6020LPQ	-91.58	48.8	389	-7.1	-6.7	-0.4	1
5733	1924-03-25	ATIKOKAN	ONT	6020LPQ	-91.58	48.8	389	2.1	2.2	-0.1	1
5734	1924-03-26	ATIKOKAN	ONT	6020LPQ	-91.58	48.8	389	0.8	2.1	-1.3	1
5735	1924-03-27	ATIKOKAN	ONT	6020LPQ	-91.58	48.8	389	-1.4	0.2	-1.6	1
5736	1924-04-05	ATIKOKAN	ONT	6020LPQ	-91.58	48.8	389	2.1	4.4	-2.3	1
5737	1924-04-08	ATIKOKAN	ONT	6020LPQ	-91.58	48.8	389	1.5	3.6	-2.1	1
5738	1924-04-09	ATIKOKAN	ONT	6020LPQ	-91.58	48.8	389	-4.8	-2.8	-2	1
5739	1924-04-13	ATIKOKAN	ONT	6020LPQ	-91.58	48.8	389	0.1	0.7	-0.6	1
5740	1924-04-16	ATIKOKAN	ONT	6020LPQ	-91.58	48.8	389	2.8	3.6	-0.8	1
5741	1924-04-17	ATIKOKAN	ONT	6020LPQ	-91.58	48.8	389	-1.9	1.4	-3.3	1
5742	1924-05-13	ATIKOKAN	ONT	6020LPQ	-91.58	48.8	389	7.6	7.8	-0.2	1
5743	1924-05-14	ATIKOKAN	ONT	6020LPQ	-91.58	48.8	389	8.1	8.8	-0.7	1
5744	1924-05-24	ATIKOKAN	ONT	6020LPQ	-91.58	48.8	389	0.8	1.4	-0.6	1
5745	1924-10-05	ATIKOKAN	ONT	6020LPQ	-91.58	48.8	389	4.5	7.7	-3.2	1

5746	1924-10-13	ATIKOKAN	ONT	6020LPQ	-91.58	48.8	389	10.7	12.2	-1.5	1
5747	1924-10-31	ATIKOKAN	ONT	6020LPQ	-91.58	48.8	389	7.6	7.7	-0.1	1
5748	1924-11-01	ATIKOKAN	ONT	6020LPQ	-91.58	48.8	389	-1.9	1.4	-3.3	1
5749	1924-11-05	ATIKOKAN	ONT	6020LPQ	-91.58	48.8	389	-3.1	0.2	-3.3	1
5750	1924-11-06	ATIKOKAN	ONT	6020LPQ	-91.58	48.8	389	-6.6	-6.1	-0.5	1
5751	1924-11-07	ATIKOKAN	ONT	6020LPQ	-91.58	48.8	389	-9	-7.7	-1.3	1
5752	1924-11-11	ATIKOKAN	ONT	6020LPQ	-91.58	48.8	389	-1.4	2.1	-3.5	1
5753	1924-11-13	ATIKOKAN	ONT	6020LPQ	-91.58	48.8	389	-5.9	-2.9	-3	1
5754	1924-11-18	ATIKOKAN	ONT	6020LPQ	-91.58	48.8	389	-9	-7.7	-1.3	1
5755	1924-11-22	ATIKOKAN	ONT	6020LPQ	-91.58	48.8	389	-5.3	-4.6	-0.7	1
5756	1924-11-23	ATIKOKAN	ONT	6020LPQ	-91.58	48.8	389	-9.5	-8.1	-1.4	1
5757	1924-11-26	ATIKOKAN	ONT	6020LPQ	-91.58	48.8	389	-6.5	-3.9	-2.6	1
5758	1924-11-27	ATIKOKAN	ONT	6020LPQ	-91.58	48.8	389	-12.7	-11.4	-1.3	1
5759	1924-11-28	ATIKOKAN	ONT	6020LPQ	-91.58	48.8	389	-13.5	-12.6	-0.9	1
5760	1924-12-07	ATIKOKAN	ONT	6020LPQ	-91.58	48.8	389	-8.3	-7.2	-1.1	1
5761	1924-12-08	ATIKOKAN	ONT	6020LPQ	-91.58	48.8	389	-12.7	-10.4	-2.3	1
5762	1924-12-09	ATIKOKAN	ONT	6020LPQ	-91.58	48.8	389	-17.4	-17.1	-0.3	1
5763	1924-12-13	ATIKOKAN	ONT	6020LPQ	-91.58	48.8	389	-21	-19.9	-1.1	1
5764	1924-12-16	ATIKOKAN	ONT	6020LPQ	-91.58	48.8	389	-24.3	-22.5	-1.8	1
5765	1924-12-21	ATIKOKAN	ONT	6020LPQ	-91.58	48.8	389	-26.5	-25.2	-1.3	1
5766	1924-12-23	ATIKOKAN	ONT	6020LPQ	-91.58	48.8	389	-20	-19	-1	1
5767	1924-12-26	ATIKOKAN	ONT	6020LPQ	-91.58	48.8	389	-22.1	-20.6	-1.5	1
5768	1925-01-03	ATIKOKAN	ONT	6020LPQ	-91.58	48.8	389	-10.1	-7.7	-2.4	1
5769	1925-01-04	ATIKOKAN	ONT	6020LPQ	-91.58	48.8	389	-12.5	-10.4	-2.1	1
5770	1925-01-07	ATIKOKAN	ONT	6020LPQ	-91.58	48.8	389	-12	-9.3	-2.7	1
5771	1925-01-21	ATIKOKAN	ONT	6020LPQ	-91.58	48.8	389	-7.8	-7.2	-0.6	1
5772	1925-01-24	ATIKOKAN	ONT	6020LPQ	-91.58	48.8	389	-12	-9.3	-2.7	1
5773	1925-01-25	ATIKOKAN	ONT	6020LPQ	-91.58	48.8	389	-23.1	-22.5	-0.6	1
5774	1925-01-31	ATIKOKAN	ONT	6020LPQ	-91.58	48.8	389	-21	-20.8	-0.2	1
5775	1925-02-07	ATIKOKAN	ONT	6020LPQ	-91.58	48.8	389	-3.1	-1.3	-1.8	1
5776	1925-02-08	ATIKOKAN	ONT	6020LPQ	-91.58	48.8	389	-12	-9.3	-2.7	1
5777	1925-02-09	ATIKOKAN	ONT	6020LPQ	-91.58	48.8	389	-13.4	-12.6	-0.8	1
5778	1925-02-13	ATIKOKAN	ONT	6020LPQ	-91.58	48.8	389	-15.3	-13.9	-1.4	1
5779	1925-02-25	ATIKOKAN	ONT	6020LPQ	-91.58	48.8	389	-17.4	-16.6	-0.8	1

5780	1925-02-26	ATIKOKAN	ONT	6020LPQ	-91.58	48.8	389	-23.1	-21.6	-1.5	1
5781	1925-03-06	ATIKOKAN	ONT	6020LPQ	-91.58	48.8	389	-2	0.2	-2.2	1
5782	1925-03-10	ATIKOKAN	ONT	6020LPQ	-91.58	48.8	389	-12.6	-10.4	-2.2	1
5783	1925-04-23	ATIKOKAN	ONT	6020LPQ	-91.58	48.8	389	4.4	7.7	-3.3	1
5784	1925-04-26	ATIKOKAN	ONT	6020LPQ	-91.58	48.8	389	4.4	6.3	-1.9	1
5785	1925-05-05	ATIKOKAN	ONT	6020LPQ	-91.58	48.8	389	-0.6	2	-2.6	1
5786	1925-05-06	ATIKOKAN	ONT	6020LPQ	-91.58	48.8	389	-1.4	1.4	-2.8	1
5787	1925-05-07	ATIKOKAN	ONT	6020LPQ	-91.58	48.8	389	-2	1.4	-3.4	1
5788	1925-05-10	ATIKOKAN	ONT	6020LPQ	-91.58	48.8	389	-0.6	0.3	-0.9	1
5789	1925-06-08	ATIKOKAN	ONT	6020LPQ	-91.58	48.8	389	15.1	15.4	-0.3	1
5790	1925-06-09	ATIKOKAN	ONT	6020LPQ	-91.58	48.8	389	5.7	8.3	-2.6	1
5791	1925-08-29	ATIKOKAN	ONT	6020LPQ	-91.58	48.8	389	16	16.5	-0.5	1
5792	1925-09-07	ATIKOKAN	ONT	6020LPQ	-91.58	48.8	389	10.7	12.2	-1.5	1
5793	1925-09-10	ATIKOKAN	ONT	6020LPQ	-91.58	48.8	389	11.4	12.9	-1.5	1
5794	1925-09-11	ATIKOKAN	ONT	6020LPQ	-91.58	48.8	389	5.7	7.3	-1.6	1
5795	1925-09-17	ATIKOKAN	ONT	6020LPQ	-91.58	48.8	389	15.1	15.9	-0.8	1
5796	1925-09-19	ATIKOKAN	ONT	6020LPQ	-91.58	48.8	389	9.6	9.7	-0.1	1
5797	1925-09-20	ATIKOKAN	ONT	6020LPQ	-91.58	48.8	389	4.5	6.8	-2.3	1
5798	1925-09-23	ATIKOKAN	ONT	6020LPQ	-91.58	48.8	389	6.1	7.8	-1.7	1
5799	1925-09-28	ATIKOKAN	ONT	6020LPQ	-91.58	48.8	389	6.7	8.3	-1.6	1
5800	1925-09-29	ATIKOKAN	ONT	6020LPQ	-91.58	48.8	389	2	2.8	-0.8	1
5801	1925-09-30	ATIKOKAN	ONT	6020LPQ	-91.58	48.8	389	3.9	5.6	-1.7	1
5802	1925-10-01	ATIKOKAN	ONT	6020LPQ	-91.58	48.8	389	2	5.1	-3.1	1
5803	1925-10-05	ATIKOKAN	ONT	6020LPQ	-91.58	48.8	389	-0.6	1.4	-2	1
5804	1925-10-06	ATIKOKAN	ONT	6020LPQ	-91.58	48.8	389	-2.6	-0.7	-1.9	1
5805	1925-10-07	ATIKOKAN	ONT	6020LPQ	-91.58	48.8	389	-3.7	-1.3	-2.4	1
5806	1925-10-08	ATIKOKAN	ONT	6020LPQ	-91.58	48.8	389	-4.2	-3.9	-0.3	1
5807	1925-10-09	ATIKOKAN	ONT	6020LPQ	-91.58	48.8	389	-3.1	-2.8	-0.3	1
5808	1925-10-11	ATIKOKAN	ONT	6020LPQ	-91.58	48.8	389	3.9	6.2	-2.3	1
5809	1925-10-14	ATIKOKAN	ONT	6020LPQ	-91.58	48.8	389	2	4.4	-2.4	1
5810	1925-10-15	ATIKOKAN	ONT	6020LPQ	-91.58	48.8	389	-0.6	1.4	-2	1
5811	1925-10-16	ATIKOKAN	ONT	6020LPQ	-91.58	48.8	389	-4.6	-2.8	-1.8	1
5812	1925-10-17	ATIKOKAN	ONT	6020LPQ	-91.58	48.8	389	-3.5	-2	-1.5	1
5813	1925-10-19	ATIKOKAN	ONT	6020LPQ	-91.58	48.8	389	-4	-3.9	-0.1	1

5814	1925-10-20	ATIKOKAN	ONT	6020LPQ	-91.58	48.8	389	-4	-3.9	-0.1	1
5815	1925-10-28	ATIKOKAN	ONT	6020LPQ	-91.58	48.8	389	-10.3	-9.4	-0.9	1
5816	1925-10-31	ATIKOKAN	ONT	6020LPQ	-91.58	48.8	389	-3.5	-2.8	-0.7	1
5817	1925-12-03	ATIKOKAN	ONT	6020LPQ	-91.58	48.8	389	-1.4	2.8	-4.2	1
5818	1925-12-04	ATIKOKAN	ONT	6020LPQ	-91.58	48.8	389	-16.6	-14.4	-2.2	1
5819	1925-12-06	ATIKOKAN	ONT	6020LPQ	-91.58	48.8	389	-13	-10.4	-2.6	1
5820	1925-12-08	ATIKOKAN	ONT	6020LPQ	-91.58	48.8	389	-18.2	-15	-3.2	1
5821	1925-12-11	ATIKOKAN	ONT	6020LPQ	-91.58	48.8	389	-10.9	-7.7	-3.2	1
5822	1925-12-12	ATIKOKAN	ONT	6020LPQ	-91.58	48.8	389	-18.2	-17.1	-1.1	1
5823	1925-12-14	ATIKOKAN	ONT	6020LPQ	-91.58	48.8	389	-21.5	-18.7	-2.8	1
5824	1925-12-16	ATIKOKAN	ONT	6020LPQ	-91.58	48.8	389	-17.6	-14.4	-3.2	1
5825	1925-12-17	ATIKOKAN	ONT	6020LPQ	-91.58	48.8	389	-18.2	-15	-3.2	1
5826	1925-12-22	ATIKOKAN	ONT	6020LPQ	-91.58	48.8	389	-23.2	-19.9	-3.3	1
5827	1925-12-24	ATIKOKAN	ONT	6020LPQ	-91.58	48.8	389	-18.2	-17.6	-0.6	1
5828	1925-12-25	ATIKOKAN	ONT	6020LPQ	-91.58	48.8	389	-24.8	-21.2	-3.6	1
5829	1925-12-28	ATIKOKAN	ONT	6020LPQ	-91.58	48.8	389	-25.4	-25.3	-0.1	1
5830	1926-02-28	ATIKOKAN	ONT	6020LPQ	-91.58	48.8	389	-4	-1.3	-2.7	1
5831	1926-03-08	ATIKOKAN	ONT	6020LPQ	-91.58	48.8	389	0.1	0.3	-0.2	1
5832	1926-08-06	ATIKOKAN	ONT	6020LPQ	-91.58	48.8	389	17.1	17.6	-0.5	1
5833	1926-08-20	ATIKOKAN	ONT	6020LPQ	-91.58	48.8	389	13.8	14.4	-0.6	1
5834	1926-09-03	ATIKOKAN	ONT	6020LPQ	-91.58	48.8	389	13.4	13.9	-0.5	1
5835	1926-09-04	ATIKOKAN	ONT	6020LPQ	-91.58	48.8	389	9.6	12.2	-2.6	1
5836	1926-09-05	ATIKOKAN	ONT	6020LPQ	-91.58	48.8	389	11.6	12.2	-0.6	1
5837	1926-10-14	ATIKOKAN	ONT	6020LPQ	-91.58	48.8	389	3.2	3.7	-0.5	1
5838	1926-10-17	ATIKOKAN	ONT	6020LPQ	-91.58	48.8	389	-1.8	-0.3	-1.5	1
5839	1926-11-02	ATIKOKAN	ONT	6020LPQ	-91.58	48.8	389	-2.9	-1.3	-1.6	1
5840	1926-11-12	ATIKOKAN	ONT	6020LPQ	-91.58	48.8	389	-4	-3.9	-0.1	1
5841	1926-11-14	ATIKOKAN	ONT	6020LPQ	-91.58	48.8	389	-1.8	0.3	-2.1	1
5842	1926-11-15	ATIKOKAN	ONT	6020LPQ	-91.58	48.8	389	-1.8	-1.3	-0.5	1
5843	1926-11-16	ATIKOKAN	ONT	6020LPQ	-91.58	48.8	389	-2.9	-1.3	-1.6	1
5844	1926-11-18	ATIKOKAN	ONT	6020LPQ	-91.58	48.8	389	-9.3	-9	-0.3	1
5845	1926-11-20	ATIKOKAN	ONT	6020LPQ	-91.58	48.8	389	-10.9	-10.4	-0.5	1
5846	1926-12-21	ATIKOKAN	ONT	6020LPQ	-91.58	48.8	389	-7.7	-7.2	-0.5	1
5847	1926-12-23	ATIKOKAN	ONT	6020LPQ	-91.58	48.8	389	-1.8	-1.3	-0.5	1

5848	1927-01-02	ATIKOKAN	ONT	6020LPQ	-91.58	48.8	389	-1.8	-1.3	-0.5	1
5849	1927-01-03	ATIKOKAN	ONT	6020LPQ	-91.58	48.8	389	-0.4	1.4	-1.8	1
5850	1927-06-21	ATIKOKAN	ONT	6020LPQ	-91.58	48.8	389	15.4	16.5	-1.1	1
5851	1927-08-28	ATIKOKAN	ONT	6020LPQ	-91.58	48.8	389	14.4	14.9	-0.5	1
5852	1927-09-30	ATIKOKAN	ONT	6020LPQ	-91.58	48.8	389	8.7	9.2	-0.5	1
5853	1927-10-02	ATIKOKAN	ONT	6020LPQ	-91.58	48.8	389	9.1	10.6	-1.5	1
5854	1927-10-03	ATIKOKAN	ONT	6020LPQ	-91.58	48.8	389	8.7	9.2	-0.5	1
5855	1927-11-01	ATIKOKAN	ONT	6020LPQ	-91.58	48.8	389	3.9	5.1	-1.2	1
5856	1927-11-05	ATIKOKAN	ONT	6020LPQ	-91.58	48.8	389	-4.6	-2.1	-2.5	1
5857	1927-11-10	ATIKOKAN	ONT	6020LPQ	-91.58	48.8	389	0.1	0.7	-0.6	1
5858	1927-12-07	ATIKOKAN	ONT	6020LPQ	-91.58	48.8	389	-24.8	-23.4	-1.4	1
5859	1927-12-08	ATIKOKAN	ONT	6020LPQ	-91.58	48.8	389	-26.5	-25.2	-1.3	1
5860	1927-12-15	ATIKOKAN	ONT	6020LPQ	-91.58	48.8	389	-13.9	-13.2	-0.7	1
5861	1927-12-22	ATIKOKAN	ONT	6020LPQ	-91.58	48.8	389	-13.5	-13.2	-0.3	1
5862	1928-01-07	ATIKOKAN	ONT	6020LPQ	-91.58	48.8	389	1.3	2.9	-1.6	1
5863	1928-01-11	ATIKOKAN	ONT	6020LPQ	-91.58	48.8	389	0.1	0.7	-0.6	1
5864	1928-01-12	ATIKOKAN	ONT	6020LPQ	-91.58	48.8	389	-0.9	2	-2.9	1
5865	1928-01-13	ATIKOKAN	ONT	6020LPQ	-91.58	48.8	389	-1.9	-1.3	-0.6	1
5866	1928-02-07	ATIKOKAN	ONT	6020LPQ	-91.58	48.8	389	-4.6	-2.1	-2.5	1
5867	1928-03-12	ATIKOKAN	ONT	6020LPQ	-91.58	48.8	389	-4	-3.8	-0.2	1
5868	1928-09-12	ATIKOKAN	ONT	6020LPQ	-91.58	48.8	389	11.6	12	-0.4	1
5869	1928-09-25	ATIKOKAN	ONT	6020LPQ	-91.58	48.8	389	4.5	5	-0.5	1
5870	1928-10-01	ATIKOKAN	ONT	6020LPQ	-91.58	48.8	389	10	10.9	-0.9	1
5871	1928-10-11	ATIKOKAN	ONT	6020LPQ	-91.58	48.8	389	7.6	7.7	-0.1	1
5872	1928-11-10	ATIKOKAN	ONT	6020LPQ	-91.58	48.8	389	-1.9	0.2	-2.1	1
5873	1928-11-11	ATIKOKAN	ONT	6020LPQ	-91.58	48.8	389	1.3	5.1	-3.8	1
5874	1928-11-16	ATIKOKAN	ONT	6020LPQ	-91.58	48.8	389	-1.4	0.7	-2.1	1
5875	1928-11-17	ATIKOKAN	ONT	6020LPQ	-91.58	48.8	389	-0.9	-0.7	-0.2	1
5876	1928-11-30	ATIKOKAN	ONT	6020LPQ	-91.58	48.8	389	-5.8	-5.3	-0.5	1
5877	1928-12-12	ATIKOKAN	ONT	6020LPQ	-91.58	48.8	389	2	3.8	-1.8	1
5878	1928-12-14	ATIKOKAN	ONT	6020LPQ	-91.58	48.8	389	-0.3	-0.2	-0.1	1
5879	1928-12-15	ATIKOKAN	ONT	6020LPQ	-91.58	48.8	389	0.1	2.9	-2.8	1
5880	1929-01-24	ATIKOKAN	ONT	6020LPQ	-91.58	48.8	389	-20.9	-19.5	-1.4	1
5881	1929-03-13	ATIKOKAN	ONT	6020LPQ	-91.58	48.8	389	1.2	3.8	-2.6	1

5882	1929-10-30	ATIKOKAN	ONT	6020LPQ	-91.58	48.8	389	-0.4	0.7	-1.1	1
5883	1929-11-05	ATIKOKAN	ONT	6020LPQ	-91.58	48.8	389	-0.4	1.3	-1.7	1
5884	1929-12-04	ATIKOKAN	ONT	6020LPQ	-91.58	48.8	389	-14	-13.2	-0.8	1
5885	1929-12-30	ATIKOKAN	ONT	6020LPQ	-91.58	48.8	389	-0.9	1.3	-2.2	1
5886	1930-01-01	ATIKOKAN	ONT	6020LPQ	-91.58	48.8	389	-2.9	-1.3	-1.6	1
5887	1930-09-16	ATIKOKAN	ONT	6020LPQ	-91.58	48.8	389	10	10.9	-0.9	1
5888	1930-11-13	ATIKOKAN	ONT	6020LPQ	-91.58	48.8	389	7.2	7.3	-0.1	1
5889	1930-11-20	ATIKOKAN	ONT	6020LPQ	-91.58	48.8	389	2.5	3	-0.5	1
5890	1930-12-07	ATIKOKAN	ONT	6020LPQ	-91.58	48.8	389	-3.5	-2.8	-0.7	1
5891	1930-12-18	ATIKOKAN	ONT	6020LPQ	-91.58	48.8	389	-4.6	-2.8	-1.8	1
5892	1931-01-09	ATIKOKAN	ONT	6020LPQ	-91.58	48.8	389	-9.9	-9.3	-0.6	1
5893	1931-02-20	ATIKOKAN	ONT	6020LPQ	-91.58	48.8	389	0.1	1.5	-1.4	1
5894	1931-02-21	ATIKOKAN	ONT	6020LPQ	-91.58	48.8	389	0.7	2.9	-2.2	1
5895	1931-03-21	ATIKOKAN	ONT	6020LPQ	-91.58	48.8	389	-1.3	1.5	-2.8	1
5896	1931-03-24	ATIKOKAN	ONT	6020LPQ	-91.58	48.8	389	0.1	0.3	-0.2	1
5897	1931-05-21	ATIKOKAN	ONT	6020LPQ	-91.58	48.8	389	1.3	1.5	-0.2	1
5898	1931-08-28	ATIKOKAN	ONT	6020LPQ	-91.58	48.8	389	10.6	11	-0.4	1
5899	1931-10-27	ATIKOKAN	ONT	6020LPQ	-91.58	48.8	389	8.7	8.8	-0.1	1
5900	1931-11-03	ATIKOKAN	ONT	6020LPQ	-91.58	48.8	389	7.7	8.8	-1.1	1
5901	1931-11-15	ATIKOKAN	ONT	6020LPQ	-91.58	48.8	389	5.1	6.2	-1.1	1
5902	1931-12-23	ATIKOKAN	ONT	6020LPQ	-91.58	48.8	389	0.1	0.7	-0.6	1
5903	1931-12-29	ATIKOKAN	ONT	6020LPQ	-91.58	48.8	389	-0.9	-0.3	-0.6	1
5904	1932-01-12	ATIKOKAN	ONT	6020LPQ	-91.58	48.8	389	-1.8	-0.3	-1.5	1
5905	1932-02-11	ATIKOKAN	ONT	6020LPQ	-91.58	48.8	389	-0.9	2.9	-3.8	1
5906	1932-04-06	ATIKOKAN	ONT	6020LPQ	-91.58	48.8	389	1.3	1.5	-0.2	1
5907	1932-05-08	ATIKOKAN	ONT	6020LPQ	-91.58	48.8	389	7.7	7.8	-0.1	1
5908	1932-10-25	ATIKOKAN	ONT	6020LPQ	-91.58	48.8	389	0.7	2.1	-1.4	1
5909	1932-11-01	ATIKOKAN	ONT	6020LPQ	-91.58	48.8	389	-1.3	-0.7	-0.6	1
5910	1932-11-07	ATIKOKAN	ONT	6020LPQ	-91.58	48.8	389	1.9	3.6	-1.7	1
5911	1932-11-08	ATIKOKAN	ONT	6020LPQ	-91.58	48.8	389	-0.4	2.1	-2.5	1
5912	1932-11-09	ATIKOKAN	ONT	6020LPQ	-91.58	48.8	389	1.3	2.9	-1.6	1
5913	1932-11-10	ATIKOKAN	ONT	6020LPQ	-91.58	48.8	389	0.7	2.9	-2.2	1
5914	1933-02-25	ATIKOKAN	ONT	6020LPQ	-91.58	48.8	389	-1.8	-1.3	-0.5	1
5915	1933-04-30	ATIKOKAN	ONT	6020LPQ	-91.58	48.8	389	3.9	5	-1.1	1

5916	1933-09-06	ATIKOKAN	ONT	6020LPQ	-91.58	48.8	389	12.1	13.5	-1.4	1
5917	1933-09-13	ATIKOKAN	ONT	6020LPQ	-91.58	48.8	389	10.6	12.1	-1.5	1
5918	1933-09-20	ATIKOKAN	ONT	6020LPQ	-91.58	48.8	389	11.6	12.9	-1.3	1
5919	1933-10-17	ATIKOKAN	ONT	6020LPQ	-91.58	48.8	389	0.7	3.7	-3	1
5920	1933-11-11	ATIKOKAN	ONT	6020LPQ	-91.58	48.8	389	-8.8	-8.2	-0.6	1
5921	1933-12-04	ATIKOKAN	ONT	6020LPQ	-91.58	48.8	389	0.1	2.1	-2	1
5922	1934-03-02	ATIKOKAN	ONT	6020LPQ	-91.58	48.8	389	3.3	4.3	-1	1
5923	1934-04-17	ATIKOKAN	ONT	6020LPQ	-91.58	48.8	389	2.5	6.8	-4.3	1
5924	1934-04-23	ATIKOKAN	ONT	6020LPQ	-91.58	48.8	389	1.3	1.4	-0.1	1
5925	1934-08-31	ATIKOKAN	ONT	6020LPQ	-91.58	48.8	389	10	12.1	-2.1	1
5926	1934-10-06	ATIKOKAN	ONT	6020LPQ	-91.58	48.8	389	9.6	10.9	-1.3	1
5927	1934-10-20	ATIKOKAN	ONT	6020LPQ	-91.58	48.8	389	6.2	6.8	-0.6	1
5928	1934-10-21	ATIKOKAN	ONT	6020LPQ	-91.58	48.8	389	7.7	8.8	-1.1	1
5929	1934-10-24	ATIKOKAN	ONT	6020LPQ	-91.58	48.8	389	9.1	10.1	-1	1
5930	1934-11-18	ATIKOKAN	ONT	6020LPQ	-91.58	48.8	389	-2.9	-2.1	-0.8	1
5931	1934-11-26	ATIKOKAN	ONT	6020LPQ	-91.58	48.8	389	0.7	2.2	-1.5	1
5932	1934-11-27	ATIKOKAN	ONT	6020LPQ	-91.58	48.8	389	-1.3	1.4	-2.7	1
5933	1934-11-29	ATIKOKAN	ONT	6020LPQ	-91.58	48.8	389	-0.9	3	-3.9	1
5934	1934-11-30	ATIKOKAN	ONT	6020LPQ	-91.58	48.8	389	-1.3	0.7	-2	1
5935	1935-02-09	ATIKOKAN	ONT	6020LPQ	-91.58	48.8	389	-5.8	-5.3	-0.5	1
5936	1935-03-03	ATIKOKAN	ONT	6020LPQ	-91.58	48.8	389	-1.8	-1.3	-0.5	1
5937	1935-03-10	ATIKOKAN	ONT	6020LPQ	-91.58	48.8	389	-1.8	-1.3	-0.5	1
5938	1935-04-18	ATIKOKAN	ONT	6020LPQ	-91.58	48.8	389	-0.9	3	-3.9	1
5939	1935-04-19	ATIKOKAN	ONT	6020LPQ	-91.58	48.8	389	0.7	2.1	-1.4	1
5940	1935-06-25	ATIKOKAN	ONT	6020LPQ	-91.58	48.8	389	19.9	20.3	-0.4	1
5941	1935-10-03	ATIKOKAN	ONT	6020LPQ	-91.58	48.8	389	1.3	1.4	-0.1	1
5942	1935-10-10	ATIKOKAN	ONT	6020LPQ	-91.58	48.8	389	1.3	1.4	-0.1	1
5943	1935-10-21	ATIKOKAN	ONT	6020LPQ	-91.58	48.8	389	5.6	7.3	-1.7	1
5944	1935-11-13	ATIKOKAN	ONT	6020LPQ	-91.58	48.8	389	-0.4	1.4	-1.8	1
5945	1935-11-14	ATIKOKAN	ONT	6020LPQ	-91.58	48.8	389	-0.9	0.2	-1.1	1
5946	1935-11-17	ATIKOKAN	ONT	6020LPQ	-91.58	48.8	389	-0.9	0.2	-1.1	1
5947	1935-11-18	ATIKOKAN	ONT	6020LPQ	-91.58	48.8	389	-2.9	-1.3	-1.6	1
5948	1935-11-24	ATIKOKAN	ONT	6020LPQ	-91.58	48.8	389	-2.4	-0.7	-1.7	1
5949	1935-11-25	ATIKOKAN	ONT	6020LPQ	-91.58	48.8	389	-2.9	-1.3	-1.6	1

5950	1935-12-06	ATIKOKAN	ONT	6020LPQ	-91.58	48.8	389	-0.4	1.4	-1.8	1
5951	1935-12-07	ATIKOKAN	ONT	6020LPQ	-91.58	48.8	389	-0.9	3	-3.9	1
5952	1935-12-08	ATIKOKAN	ONT	6020LPQ	-91.58	48.8	389	-1.3	1.4	-2.7	1
5953	1935-12-09	ATIKOKAN	ONT	6020LPQ	-91.58	48.8	389	-0.9	0.2	-1.1	1
5954	1935-12-12	ATIKOKAN	ONT	6020LPQ	-91.58	48.8	389	-2.9	-1.3	-1.6	1
5955	1935-12-30	ATIKOKAN	ONT	6020LPQ	-91.58	48.8	389	-9.9	-9	-0.9	1
5956	1936-03-19	ATIKOKAN	ONT	6020LPQ	-91.58	48.8	389	7.7	9.2	-1.5	1
5957	1936-03-23	ATIKOKAN	ONT	6020LPQ	-91.58	48.8	389	0.7	1.5	-0.8	1
5958	1936-03-24	ATIKOKAN	ONT	6020LPQ	-91.58	48.8	389	0.7	3	-2.3	1
5959	1936-04-14	ATIKOKAN	ONT	6020LPQ	-91.58	48.8	389	-0.9	0.7	-1.6	1
5960	1936-04-15	ATIKOKAN	ONT	6020LPQ	-91.58	48.8	389	3.3	4.3	-1	1
5961	1936-06-13	ATIKOKAN	ONT	6020LPQ	-91.58	48.8	389	23.8	24.2	-0.4	1
5962	1936-06-28	ATIKOKAN	ONT	6020LPQ	-91.58	48.8	389	23.8	24.8	-1	1
5963	1936-10-25	ATIKOKAN	ONT	6020LPQ	-91.58	48.8	389	-2.9	-1.3	-1.6	1
5964	1936-10-28	ATIKOKAN	ONT	6020LPQ	-91.58	48.8	389	-1.8	-0.3	-1.5	1
5965	1936-12-30	ATIKOKAN	ONT	6020LPQ	-91.58	48.8	389	0.1	3.6	-3.5	1
5966	1937-02-08	ATIKOKAN	ONT	6020LPQ	-91.58	48.8	389	-16.6	-16.1	-0.5	1
5967	1937-04-05	ATIKOKAN	ONT	6020LPQ	-91.58	48.8	389	-0.4	-0.3	-0.1	1
5968	1937-04-25	ATIKOKAN	ONT	6020LPQ	-91.58	48.8	389	4.5	7.3	-2.8	1
5969	1937-05-22	ATIKOKAN	ONT	6020LPQ	-91.58	48.8	389	8.1	8.8	-0.7	1
5970	1937-07-15	ATIKOKAN	ONT	6020LPQ	-91.58	48.8	389	17.1	18.1	-1	1
5971	1937-07-16	ATIKOKAN	ONT	6020LPQ	-91.58	48.8	389	17.1	18.7	-1.6	1
5972	1937-09-27	ATIKOKAN	ONT	6020LPQ	-91.58	48.8	389	8.2	9.1	-0.9	1
5973	1937-10-18	ATIKOKAN	ONT	6020LPQ	-91.58	48.8	389	6.7	7.3	-0.6	1
5974	1937-10-19	ATIKOKAN	ONT	6020LPQ	-91.58	48.8	389	6.7	6.8	-0.1	1
5975	1937-10-20	ATIKOKAN	ONT	6020LPQ	-91.58	48.8	389	3.2	4.4	-1.2	1
5976	1937-11-08	ATIKOKAN	ONT	6020LPQ	-91.58	48.8	389	-1.8	-0.7	-1.1	1
5977	1937-11-11	ATIKOKAN	ONT	6020LPQ	-91.58	48.8	389	4	5.6	-1.6	1
5978	1937-11-24	ATIKOKAN	ONT	6020LPQ	-91.58	48.8	389	-2.9	-1.3	-1.6	1
5979	1937-11-25	ATIKOKAN	ONT	6020LPQ	-91.58	48.8	389	-0.4	1.3	-1.7	1
5980	1937-11-26	ATIKOKAN	ONT	6020LPQ	-91.58	48.8	389	-0.4	1.3	-1.7	1
5981	1938-03-12	ATIKOKAN	ONT	6020LPQ	-91.58	48.8	389	3.2	3.7	-0.5	1
5982	1938-04-27	ATIKOKAN	ONT	6020LPQ	-91.58	48.8	389	6.7	8.8	-2.1	1
5983	1938-05-02	ATIKOKAN	ONT	6020LPQ	-91.58	48.8	389	5.6	7.7	-2.1	1

5984	1938-11-05	ATIKOKAN	ONT	6020LPQ	-91.58	48.8	389	-0.4	0.2	-0.6	1
5985	1938-12-03	ATIKOKAN	ONT	6020LPQ	-91.58	48.8	389	-1.8	-0.3	-1.5	1
5986	1938-12-12	ATIKOKAN	ONT	6020LPQ	-91.58	48.8	389	-8.2	-8.1	-0.1	1
5987	1939-01-04	ATIKOKAN	ONT	6020LPQ	-91.58	48.8	389	-4.6	-1.3	-3.3	1
5988	1939-02-12	ATIKOKAN	ONT	6020LPQ	-91.58	48.8	389	-18.7	-18.6	-0.1	1
5989	1939-10-05	ATIKOKAN	ONT	6020LPQ	-91.58	48.8	389	10	10.1	-0.1	1
5990	1939-10-12	ATIKOKAN	ONT	6020LPQ	-91.58	48.8	389	-0.9	-0.3	-0.6	1
5991	1939-10-31	ATIKOKAN	ONT	6020LPQ	-91.58	48.8	389	-0.9	0.2	-1.1	1
5992	1939-11-26	ATIKOKAN	ONT	6020LPQ	-91.58	48.8	389	0.1	0.7	-0.6	1
5993	1939-12-17	ATIKOKAN	ONT	6020LPQ	-91.58	48.8	389	-1.9	-1.4	-0.5	1
5994	1939-12-18	ATIKOKAN	ONT	6020LPQ	-91.58	48.8	389	-1.9	0.2	-2.1	1
5995	1940-02-17	ATIKOKAN	ONT	6020LPQ	-91.58	48.8	389	-2.9	-1.4	-1.5	1
5996	1940-03-02	ATIKOKAN	ONT	6020LPQ	-91.58	48.8	389	-4	-3	-1	1
5997	1940-03-04	ATIKOKAN	ONT	6020LPQ	-91.58	48.8	389	-2.4	-2	-0.4	1
5998	1940-05-19	ATIKOKAN	ONT	6020LPQ	-91.58	48.8	389	10	11	-1	1
5999	1940-10-30	ATIKOKAN	ONT	6020LPQ	-91.58	48.8	389	3.9	5.6	-1.7	1
6000	1940-10-31	ATIKOKAN	ONT	6020LPQ	-91.58	48.8	389	4.5	6.2	-1.7	1
6001	1940-11-02	ATIKOKAN	ONT	6020LPQ	-91.58	48.8	389	3.9	5.1	-1.2	1
6002	1940-11-04	ATIKOKAN	ONT	6020LPQ	-91.58	48.8	389	3.9	5.1	-1.2	1
6003	1940-11-08	ATIKOKAN	ONT	6020LPQ	-91.58	48.8	389	-1.3	0.3	-1.6	1
6004	1940-11-10	ATIKOKAN	ONT	6020LPQ	-91.58	48.8	389	-6.4	-6.1	-0.3	1
6005	1940-11-11	ATIKOKAN	ONT	6020LPQ	-91.58	48.8	389	-7.1	-3.9	-3.2	1
6006	1940-11-17	ATIKOKAN	ONT	6020LPQ	-91.58	48.8	389	1.3	2	-0.7	1
6007	1940-11-19	ATIKOKAN	ONT	6020LPQ	-91.58	48.8	389	0.7	1.3	-0.6	1
6008	1941-02-01	ATIKOKAN	ONT	6020LPQ	-91.58	48.8	389	-5.9	-5.5	-0.4	1
6009	1941-09-13	ATIKOKAN	ONT	6020LPQ	-91.58	48.8	389	13.4	13.5	-0.1	1
6010	1941-09-28	ATIKOKAN	ONT	6020LPQ	-91.58	48.8	389	7.2	7.3	-0.1	1
6011	1941-11-17	ATIKOKAN	ONT	6020LPQ	-91.58	48.8	389	3.2	3.7	-0.5	1
6012	1941-12-17	ATIKOKAN	ONT	6020LPQ	-91.58	48.8	389	-2.9	0.2	-3.1	1
6013	1941-12-22	ATIKOKAN	ONT	6020LPQ	-91.58	48.8	389	-0.9	-0.7	-0.2	1
6014	1942-02-04	ATIKOKAN	ONT	6020LPQ	-91.58	48.8	389	-8.2	-8.1	-0.1	1
6015	1942-05-18	ATIKOKAN	ONT	6020LPQ	-91.58	48.8	389	7.5	7.8	-0.3	1
6016	1942-10-31	ATIKOKAN	ONT	6020LPQ	-91.58	48.8	389	0.4	0.7	-0.3	1
6017	1942-12-23	ATIKOKAN	ONT	6020LPQ	-91.58	48.8	389	-9.1	-6.7	-2.4	1

6018	1943-01-09	ATIKOKAN	ONT	6020LPQ	-91.58	48.8	389	-10.8	-10.3	-0.5	1
6019	1943-01-12	ATIKOKAN	ONT	6020LPQ	-91.58	48.8	389	-13.3	-12.1	-1.2	1
6020	1943-05-06	ATIKOKAN	ONT	6020LPQ	-91.58	48.8	389	6.9	7.3	-0.4	1
6021	1943-10-22	ATIKOKAN	ONT	6020LPQ	-91.58	48.8	389	7.5	8.3	-0.8	1
6022	1943-11-01	ATIKOKAN	ONT	6020LPQ	-91.58	48.8	389	2.5	2.9	-0.4	1
6023	1943-11-03	ATIKOKAN	ONT	6020LPQ	-91.58	48.8	389	0.8	1.4	-0.6	1
6024	1943-11-26	ATIKOKAN	ONT	6020LPQ	-91.58	48.8	389	-6.3	-5.5	-0.8	1
6025	1944-03-13	ATIKOKAN	ONT	6020LPQ	-91.58	48.8	389	-5.5	-5.3	-0.2	1
6026	1944-11-13	ATIKOKAN	ONT	6020LPQ	-91.58	48.8	389	5.3	6.8	-1.5	1
6027	1945-01-19	ATIKOKAN	ONT	6020LPQ	-91.58	48.8	389	-5.5	-5.3	-0.2	1
6028	1945-04-17	ATIKOKAN	ONT	6020LPQ	-91.58	48.8	389	1.4	3.8	-2.4	1
6029	1946-10-05	ATIKOKAN	ONT	6020LPQ	-91.58	48.8	389	8	10	-2	1
6030	1946-10-12	ATIKOKAN	ONT	6020LPQ	-91.58	48.8	389	-2.8	-2.1	-0.7	1
6031	1946-12-08	ATIKOKAN	ONT	6020LPQ	-91.58	48.8	389	0.3	0.7	-0.4	1
6032	1947-09-18	ATIKOKAN	ONT	6020LPQ	-91.58	48.8	389	8.6	9.7	-1.1	1
6033	1947-09-19	ATIKOKAN	ONT	6020LPQ	-91.58	48.8	389	8	9.7	-1.7	1
6034	1947-10-25	ATIKOKAN	ONT	6020LPQ	-91.58	48.8	389	5.3	8.7	-3.4	1
6035	1947-10-26	ATIKOKAN	ONT	6020LPQ	-91.58	48.8	389	8.6	9.2	-0.6	1
6036	1947-10-31	ATIKOKAN	ONT	6020LPQ	-91.58	48.8	389	4.2	7.3	-3.1	1
6037	1947-11-05	ATIKOKAN	ONT	6020LPQ	-91.58	48.8	389	6.9	8.7	-1.8	1
6038	1947-11-07	ATIKOKAN	ONT	6020LPQ	-91.58	48.8	389	0.4	2	-1.6	1
6039	1947-11-21	ATIKOKAN	ONT	6020LPQ	-91.58	48.8	389	0.8	2.8	-2	1
6040	1947-12-14	ATIKOKAN	ONT	6020LPQ	-91.58	48.8	389	-6.2	-6.1	-0.1	1
6041	1948-03-21	ATIKOKAN	ONT	6020LPQ	-91.58	48.8	389	-2.2	1.4	-3.6	1
6042	1948-04-23	ATIKOKAN	ONT	6020LPQ	-91.58	48.8	389	8	8.7	-0.7	1
6043	1948-08-11	ATIKOKAN	ONT	6020LPQ	-91.58	48.8	389	14.2	14.9	-0.7	1
6044	1948-10-22	ATIKOKAN	ONT	6020LPQ	-91.58	48.8	389	7.5	7.8	-0.3	1
6045	1948-10-31	ATIKOKAN	ONT	6020LPQ	-91.58	48.8	389	10.3	10.6	-0.3	1
6046	1948-11-04	ATIKOKAN	ONT	6020LPQ	-91.58	48.8	389	8.6	9.1	-0.5	1
6047	1948-11-05	ATIKOKAN	ONT	6020LPQ	-91.58	48.8	389	7.5	9.1	-1.6	1
6048	1948-11-07	ATIKOKAN	ONT	6020LPQ	-91.58	48.8	389	4.2	7.3	-3.1	1
6049	1948-11-17	ATIKOKAN	ONT	6020LPQ	-91.58	48.8	389	-0.2	0.7	-0.9	1
6050	1948-11-26	ATIKOKAN	ONT	6020LPQ	-91.58	48.8	389	-3.4	-2.9	-0.5	1
6051	1948-12-05	ATIKOKAN	ONT	6020LPQ	-91.58	48.8	389	0.8	2.9	-2.1	1

6052	1949-03-20	ATIKOKAN	ONT	6020LPQ	-91.58	48.8	389	-19.2	-16.6	-2.6	1
6053	1949-03-25	ATIKOKAN	ONT	6020LPQ	-91.58	48.8	389	0.4	1.4	-1	1
6054	1949-03-26	ATIKOKAN	ONT	6020LPQ	-91.58	48.8	389	0.8	2.1	-1.3	1
6055	1949-03-27	ATIKOKAN	ONT	6020LPQ	-91.58	48.8	389	0.8	1.4	-0.6	1
6056	1949-09-12	ATIKOKAN	ONT	6020LPQ	-91.58	48.8	389	13	13.2	-0.2	1
6057	1949-10-08	ATIKOKAN	ONT	6020LPQ	-91.58	48.8	389	7.5	10.1	-2.6	1
6058	1949-10-22	ATIKOKAN	ONT	6020LPQ	-91.58	48.8	389	-0.6	1.4	-2	1
6059	1949-10-25	ATIKOKAN	ONT	6020LPQ	-91.58	48.8	389	-0.6	-0.2	-0.4	1
6060	1949-11-04	ATIKOKAN	ONT	6020LPQ	-91.58	48.8	389	-1.2	-0.2	-1	1
6061	1949-11-10	ATIKOKAN	ONT	6020LPQ	-91.58	48.8	389	3	3.6	-0.6	1
6062	1949-11-11	ATIKOKAN	ONT	6020LPQ	-91.58	48.8	389	2.5	2.8	-0.3	1
6063	1949-11-12	ATIKOKAN	ONT	6020LPQ	-91.58	48.8	389	0.8	2.8	-2	1
6064	1949-11-15	ATIKOKAN	ONT	6020LPQ	-91.58	48.8	389	-2.2	-1.4	-0.8	1
6065	1949-11-18	ATIKOKAN	ONT	6020LPQ	-91.58	48.8	389	-2.2	-1.4	-0.8	1
6066	1949-12-17	ATIKOKAN	ONT	6020LPQ	-91.58	48.8	389	-8.5	-8	-0.5	1
6067	1949-12-18	ATIKOKAN	ONT	6020LPQ	-91.58	48.8	389	-7.8	-6.1	-1.7	1
6068	1950-05-05	ATIKOKAN	ONT	6020LPQ	-91.58	48.8	389	4.7	6.2	-1.5	1
6069	1950-09-13	ATIKOKAN	ONT	6020LPQ	-91.58	48.8	389	11.9	12	-0.1	1
6070	1950-10-24	ATIKOKAN	ONT	6020LPQ	-91.58	48.8	389	3.6	3.8	-0.2	1
6071	1950-11-06	ATIKOKAN	ONT	6020LPQ	-91.58	48.8	389	0.4	0.7	-0.3	1
6072	1950-11-07	ATIKOKAN	ONT	6020LPQ	-91.58	48.8	389	-0.7	-0.2	-0.5	1
6073	1950-11-08	ATIKOKAN	ONT	6020LPQ	-91.58	48.8	389	-1.2	-0.2	-1	1
6074	1951-01-11	ATIKOKAN	ONT	6020LPQ	-91.58	48.8	389	-7	-6.7	-0.3	1
6075	1951-02-18	ATIKOKAN	ONT	6020LPQ	-91.58	48.8	389	1.4	3.6	-2.2	1
6076	1951-02-25	ATIKOKAN	ONT	6020LPQ	-91.58	48.8	389	1.9	4.3	-2.4	1
6077	1951-03-27	ATIKOKAN	ONT	6020LPQ	-91.58	48.8	389	2.5	3.7	-1.2	1
6078	1951-04-02	ATIKOKAN	ONT	6020LPQ	-91.58	48.8	389	1.4	3.7	-2.3	1
6079	1951-04-28	ATIKOKAN	ONT	6020LPQ	-91.58	48.8	389	9.2	9.6	-0.4	1
6080	1951-05-27	ATIKOKAN	ONT	6020LPQ	-91.58	48.8	389	11.4	11.8	-0.4	1
6081	1951-09-22	ATIKOKAN	ONT	6020LPQ	-91.58	48.8	389	8.6	8.7	-0.1	1
6082	1951-09-27	ATIKOKAN	ONT	6020LPQ	-91.58	48.8	389	1.9	3	-1.1	1
6083	1951-10-03	ATIKOKAN	ONT	6020LPQ	-91.58	48.8	389	11.4	11.8	-0.4	1
6084	1951-10-05	ATIKOKAN	ONT	6020LPQ	-91.58	48.8	389	5.8	6.2	-0.4	1
6085	1951-10-21	ATIKOKAN	ONT	6020LPQ	-91.58	48.8	389	2.5	5.1	-2.6	1

6086	1951-11-12	ATIKOKAN	ONT	6020LPQ	-91.58	48.8	389	4.7	5.1	-0.4	1
6087	1951-11-16	ATIKOKAN	ONT	6020LPQ	-91.58	48.8	389	-7.8	-7.2	-0.6	1
6088	1951-12-03	ATIKOKAN	ONT	6020LPQ	-91.58	48.8	389	4.2	8.3	-4.1	1
6089	1951-12-06	ATIKOKAN	ONT	6020LPQ	-91.58	48.8	389	0.4	0.7	-0.3	1
6090	1951-12-07	ATIKOKAN	ONT	6020LPQ	-91.58	48.8	389	-2.2	-0.7	-1.5	1
6091	1951-12-08	ATIKOKAN	ONT	6020LPQ	-91.58	48.8	389	-4.7	-3.9	-0.8	1
6092	1952-02-03	ATIKOKAN	ONT	6020LPQ	-91.58	48.8	389	-2.2	-0.7	-1.5	1
6093	1952-02-04	ATIKOKAN	ONT	6020LPQ	-91.58	48.8	389	-7.9	-5.5	-2.4	1
6094	1952-03-19	ATIKOKAN	ONT	6020LPQ	-91.58	48.8	389	2.5	4.3	-1.8	1
6095	1952-03-20	ATIKOKAN	ONT	6020LPQ	-91.58	48.8	389	0.8	1.4	-0.6	1
6096	1952-04-02	ATIKOKAN	ONT	6020LPQ	-91.58	48.8	389	-1.2	0.3	-1.5	1
6097	1952-04-03	ATIKOKAN	ONT	6020LPQ	-91.58	48.8	389	-0.2	0.3	-0.5	1
6098	1952-04-04	ATIKOKAN	ONT	6020LPQ	-91.58	48.8	389	-2.8	0.3	-3.1	1
6099	1952-05-11	ATIKOKAN	ONT	6020LPQ	-91.58	48.8	389	8	9.2	-1.2	1
6100	1952-06-24	ATIKOKAN	ONT	6020LPQ	-91.58	48.8	389	19.2	20.3	-1.1	1
6101	1952-10-14	ATIKOKAN	ONT	6020LPQ	-91.58	48.8	389	3	7.3	-4.3	1
6102	1952-11-16	ATIKOKAN	ONT	6020LPQ	-91.58	48.8	389	1.9	2.1	-0.2	1
6103	1952-11-17	ATIKOKAN	ONT	6020LPQ	-91.58	48.8	389	2.5	5.1	-2.6	1
6104	1952-12-03	ATIKOKAN	ONT	6020LPQ	-91.58	48.8	389	-1.2	0.3	-1.5	1
6105	1952-12-04	ATIKOKAN	ONT	6020LPQ	-91.58	48.8	389	-1.2	0.7	-1.9	1
6106	1952-12-05	ATIKOKAN	ONT	6020LPQ	-91.58	48.8	389	-2.2	-0.3	-1.9	1
6107	1952-12-23	ATIKOKAN	ONT	6020LPQ	-91.58	48.8	389	-1.2	-0.3	-0.9	1
6108	1953-01-01	ATIKOKAN	ONT	6020LPQ	-91.58	48.8	389	-4.7	-2.9	-1.8	1
6109	1953-01-18	ATIKOKAN	ONT	6020LPQ	-91.58	48.8	389	-10.3	-7.2	-3.1	1
6110	1953-01-21	ATIKOKAN	ONT	6020LPQ	-91.58	48.8	389	-9.1	-8.5	-0.6	1
6111	1953-03-11	ATIKOKAN	ONT	6020LPQ	-91.58	48.8	389	3.6	4.4	-0.8	1
6112	1953-03-15	ATIKOKAN	ONT	6020LPQ	-91.58	48.8	389	-1.2	-0.7	-0.5	1
6113	1954-04-07	ATIKOKAN	ONT	6020LPQ	-91.58	48.8	389	-4.7	-3.8	-0.9	1
6114	1954-06-08	ATIKOKAN	ONT	6020LPQ	-91.58	48.8	389	22.7	24.2	-1.5	1
6115	1954-11-20	ATIKOKAN	ONT	6020LPQ	-91.58	48.8	389	-0.6	0.2	-0.8	1
6116	1954-11-21	ATIKOKAN	ONT	6020LPQ	-91.58	48.8	389	-0.6	-0.2	-0.4	1
6117	1955-02-20	ATIKOKAN	ONT	6020LPQ	-91.58	48.8	389	-8.4	-8.1	-0.3	1
6118	1955-05-28	ATIKOKAN	ONT	6020LPQ	-91.58	48.8	389	9.2	9.7	-0.5	1
6119	1955-07-26	ATIKOKAN	ONT	6020LPQ	-91.58	48.8	389	14.3	14.4	-0.1	1

6120	1955-11-16	ATIKOKAN	ONT	6020LPQ	-91.58	48.8	389	-6.3	-6.1	-0.2	1
6121	1955-11-20	ATIKOKAN	ONT	6020LPQ	-91.58	48.8	389	-9.1	-8	-1.1	1
6122	1956-05-11	ATIKOKAN	ONT	6020LPQ	-91.58	48.8	389	9.7	11.3	-1.6	1
6123	1959-01-02	ATIKOKAN	ONT	6020LPQ	-91.58	48.8	389	-22.6	-21.6	-1	1
6124	1959-10-30	ATIKOKAN	ONT	6020LPQ	-91.58	48.8	389	3	3.7	-0.7	1
6125	1960-04-14	ATIKOKAN	ONT	6020LPQ	-91.58	48.8	389	10.8	12	-1.2	1
6126	1960-10-30	ATIKOKAN	ONT	6020LPQ	-91.58	48.8	389	6.9	8.3	-1.4	1
6127	1960-10-31	ATIKOKAN	ONT	6020LPQ	-91.58	48.8	389	6.9	9.2	-2.3	1
6128	1960-11-13	ATIKOKAN	ONT	6020LPQ	-91.58	48.8	389	-1.2	-0.2	-1	1
6129	1960-11-29	ATIKOKAN	ONT	6020LPQ	-91.58	48.8	389	-10.3	-9.4	-0.9	1
6130	1960-12-18	ATIKOKAN	ONT	6020LPQ	-91.58	48.8	389	-14.9	-13.8	-1.1	1
6131	1961-01-20	ATIKOKAN	ONT	6020LPQ	-91.58	48.8	389	-23.1	-22.9	-0.2	1
6132	1961-04-16	ATIKOKAN	ONT	6020LPQ	-91.58	48.8	389	0.9	1.5	-0.6	1
6133	1961-10-13	ATIKOKAN	ONT	6020LPQ	-91.58	48.8	389	4.7	5.6	-0.9	1
6134	1961-11-02	ATIKOKAN	ONT	6020LPQ	-91.58	48.8	389	4.2	4.4	-0.2	1
6135	1961-11-07	ATIKOKAN	ONT	6020LPQ	-91.58	48.8	389	-5.5	-2.9	-2.6	1
6136	1961-11-15	ATIKOKAN	ONT	6020LPQ	-91.58	48.8	389	0.8	1.4	-0.6	1
6137	1961-11-22	ATIKOKAN	ONT	6020LPQ	-91.58	48.8	389	-1.2	0.3	-1.5	1
6138	1961-12-02	ATIKOKAN	ONT	6020LPQ	-91.58	48.8	389	-2.8	-2	-0.8	1
6139	1962-02-13	ATIKOKAN	ONT	6020LPQ	-91.58	48.8	389	-4.1	-2.9	-1.2	1
6140	1962-03-26	ATIKOKAN	ONT	6020LPQ	-91.58	48.8	389	2.5	2.8	-0.3	1
6141	1962-03-28	ATIKOKAN	ONT	6020LPQ	-91.58	48.8	389	0.9	3.8	-2.9	1
6142	1962-10-30	ATIKOKAN	ONT	6020LPQ	-91.58	48.8	389	4.7	5.1	-0.4	1
6143	1962-11-13	ATIKOKAN	ONT	6020LPQ	-91.58	48.8	389	-7.8	-0.7	-7.1	1
6144	1962-11-14	ATIKOKAN	ONT	6020LPQ	-91.58	48.8	389	-6.1	-0.3	-5.8	1
6145	1962-11-15	ATIKOKAN	ONT	6020LPQ	-91.58	48.8	389	-3.3	1.4	-4.7	1
6146	1963-01-07	ATIKOKAN	ONT	6020LPQ	-91.58	48.8	389	-1.8	-1.3	-0.5	1
6147	1963-11-08	ATIKOKAN	ONT	6020LPQ	-91.58	48.8	389	7.5	7.8	-0.3	1
6148	1963-11-09	ATIKOKAN	ONT	6020LPQ	-91.58	48.8	389	6.9	7.3	-0.4	1
6149	1963-11-13	ATIKOKAN	ONT	6020LPQ	-91.58	48.8	389	-1.2	-0.7	-0.5	1
6150	1964-02-12	ATIKOKAN	ONT	6020LPQ	-91.58	48.8	389	-1.2	-0.7	-0.5	1
6151	1964-04-06	ATIKOKAN	ONT	6020LPQ	-91.58	48.8	389	0.4	0.7	-0.3	1
6152	1964-05-01	ATIKOKAN	ONT	6020LPQ	-91.58	48.8	389	9.2	9.7	-0.5	1
6153	1964-07-08	ATIKOKAN	ONT	6020LPQ	-91.58	48.8	389	19.6	20.3	-0.7	1

6154	1964-09-23	ATIKOKAN	ONT	6020LPQ	-91.58	48.8	389	8	10.9	-2.9	1
6155	1964-09-26	ATIKOKAN	ONT	6020LPQ	-91.58	48.8	389	4.7	7.3	-2.6	1
6156	1964-10-04	ATIKOKAN	ONT	6020LPQ	-91.58	48.8	389	2.5	2.8	-0.3	1
6157	1964-10-07	ATIKOKAN	ONT	6020LPQ	-91.58	48.8	389	3	3.7	-0.7	1
6158	1964-11-11	ATIKOKAN	ONT	6020LPQ	-91.58	48.8	389	4.7	5.6	-0.9	1
6159	1964-11-14	ATIKOKAN	ONT	6020LPQ	-91.58	48.8	389	0.8	1.5	-0.7	1
6160	1964-12-10	ATIKOKAN	ONT	6020LPQ	-91.58	48.8	389	-1.2	-0.7	-0.5	1
6161	1964-12-29	ATIKOKAN	ONT	6020LPQ	-91.58	48.8	389	-7.8	-7.2	-0.6	1
6162	1965-09-18	ATIKOKAN	ONT	6020LPQ	-91.58	48.8	389	9.2	9.7	-0.5	1
6163	1965-10-07	ATIKOKAN	ONT	6020LPQ	-91.58	48.8	389	10.3	11	-0.7	1
6164	1965-10-08	ATIKOKAN	ONT	6020LPQ	-91.58	48.8	389	9.2	10.5	-1.3	1
6165	1965-10-09	ATIKOKAN	ONT	6020LPQ	-91.58	48.8	389	6.9	8.7	-1.8	1
6166	1965-10-11	ATIKOKAN	ONT	6020LPQ	-91.58	48.8	389	4.2	4.3	-0.1	1
6167	1965-11-12	ATIKOKAN	ONT	6020LPQ	-91.58	48.8	389	-0.2	3.7	-3.9	1
6168	1965-11-22	ATIKOKAN	ONT	6020LPQ	-91.58	48.8	389	-0.6	0.2	-0.8	1
6169	1965-11-27	ATIKOKAN	ONT	6020LPQ	-91.58	48.8	389	-7.9	-7.7	-0.2	1
6170	1965-11-28	ATIKOKAN	ONT	6020LPQ	-91.58	48.8	389	-7.8	-6.7	-1.1	1
6171	1965-12-14	ATIKOKAN	ONT	6020LPQ	-91.58	48.8	389	-10.3	-9	-1.3	1
6172	1965-12-16	ATIKOKAN	ONT	6020LPQ	-91.58	48.8	389	-11.8	-9.9	-1.9	1
6173	1965-12-20	ATIKOKAN	ONT	6020LPQ	-91.58	48.8	389	-8.5	-6.1	-2.4	1
6174	1965-12-21	ATIKOKAN	ONT	6020LPQ	-91.58	48.8	389	-4.6	-0.7	-3.9	1
6175	1965-12-28	ATIKOKAN	ONT	6020LPQ	-91.58	48.8	389	-8.5	-3	-5.5	1
6176	1966-01-06	ATIKOKAN	ONT	6020LPQ	-91.58	48.8	389	-28.1	-24.3	-3.8	1
6177	1966-01-10	ATIKOKAN	ONT	6020LPQ	-91.58	48.8	389	-22.6	-21.5	-1.1	1
6178	1966-01-27	ATIKOKAN	ONT	6020LPQ	-91.58	48.8	389	-32	-31.1	-0.9	1
6179	1966-02-01	ATIKOKAN	ONT	6020LPQ	-91.58	48.8	389	-12.3	-12.1	-0.2	1
6180	1966-02-17	ATIKOKAN	ONT	6020LPQ	-91.58	48.8	389	-28.1	-27.6	-0.5	1
6181	1966-04-01	ATIKOKAN	ONT	6020LPQ	-91.58	48.8	389	0.8	2.8	-2	1
6182	1966-05-20	ATIKOKAN	ONT	6020LPQ	-91.58	48.8	389	9.2	10.5	-1.3	1
6183	1966-08-09	ATIKOKAN	ONT	6020LPQ	-91.58	48.8	389	11.9	12.9	-1	1
6184	1966-10-03	ATIKOKAN	ONT	6020LPQ	-91.58	48.8	389	7.8	8.1	-0.3	1
6185	1967-12-06	ATIKOKAN	ONT	6020LPQ	-91.58	48.8	389	1.7	2.8	-1.1	1
6186	1968-04-21	ATIKOKAN	ONT	6020LPQ	-91.58	48.8	389	6.7	7.5	-0.8	1
6187	1968-10-18	ATIKOKAN	ONT	6020LPQ	-91.58	48.8	389	7.2	7.5	-0.3	1

6188	1969-01-24	ATIKOKAN	ONT	6020LPQ	-91.58	48.8	389	-20	-18.7	-1.3	1
6189	1969-11-01	ATIKOKAN	ONT	6020LPQ	-91.58	48.8	389	2.2	2.8	-0.6	1
6190	1969-11-02	ATIKOKAN	ONT	6020LPQ	-91.58	48.8	389	1.7	2.2	-0.5	1
6191	1970-04-28	ATIKOKAN	ONT	6020LPQ	-91.58	48.8	389	6.7	7.5	-0.8	1
6192	1970-10-08	ATIKOKAN	ONT	6020LPQ	-91.58	48.8	389	1.7	2.2	-0.5	1
6193	1970-10-24	ATIKOKAN	ONT	6020LPQ	-91.58	48.8	389	11.7	11.9	-0.2	1
6194	1970-11-16	ATIKOKAN	ONT	6020LPQ	-91.58	48.8	389	1.1	1.5	-0.4	1
6195	1970-11-18	ATIKOKAN	ONT	6020LPQ	-91.58	48.8	389	1.7	2.2	-0.5	1
6196	1971-11-15	ATIKOKAN	ONT	6020LPQ	-91.58	48.8	389	2.8	4.1	-1.3	1
6197	1971-11-17	ATIKOKAN	ONT	6020LPQ	-91.58	48.8	389	1.7	2.2	-0.5	1
6198	1972-11-10	ATIKOKAN	ONT	6020LPQ	-91.58	48.8	389	2.2	2.8	-0.6	1
6199	1973-03-07	ATIKOKAN	ONT	6020LPQ	-91.58	48.8	389	1.7	2.2	-0.5	1
6200	1973-06-28	ATIKOKAN	ONT	6020LPQ	-91.58	48.8	389	11.1	11.6	-0.5	1
6201	1974-04-13	ATIKOKAN	ONT	6020LPQ	-91.58	48.8	389	0.6	1	-0.4	1
6202	1975-09-19	ATIKOKAN	ONT	6020LPQ	-91.58	48.8	389	10	10.1	-0.1	1
6203	1977-03-13	ATIKOKAN	ONT	6020LPQ	-91.58	48.8	389	2.4	2.7	-0.3	1
6204	1977-09-26	ATIKOKAN	ONT	6020LPQ	-91.58	48.8	389	12.2	12.6	-0.4	1
6205	1977-11-07	ATIKOKAN	ONT	6020LPQ	-91.58	48.8	389	9.1	9.4	-0.3	1
6206	1977-11-16	ATIKOKAN	ONT	6020LPQ	-91.58	48.8	389	0.3	1.2	-0.9	1
6207	1977-12-17	ATIKOKAN	ONT	6020LPQ	-91.58	48.8	389	2.3	2.9	-0.6	1
6208	1978-09-29	ATIKOKAN	ONT	6020LPQ	-91.58	48.8	389	9.5	11	-1.5	1
6209	1978-10-25	ATIKOKAN	ONT	6020LPQ	-91.58	48.8	389	1.1	3.2	-2.1	1
6210	1979-03-18	ATIKOKAN	ONT	6020LPQ	-91.58	48.8	389	4.1	4.4	-0.3	1
6211	1979-10-27	ATIKOKAN	ONT	6020LPQ	-91.58	48.8	389	1.4	2.3	-0.9	1
6212	1979-10-28	ATIKOKAN	ONT	6020LPQ	-91.58	48.8	389	2.5	3	-0.5	1
6213	1996-01-17	ATIKOKAN	ONT	6020LPQ	-91.58	48.8	389	-22	-20	-2	1
6214	1996-01-18	ATIKOKAN	ONT	6020LPQ	-91.58	48.8	389	-23.5	-23	-0.5	1
6215	1996-01-29	ATIKOKAN	ONT	6020LPQ	-91.58	48.8	389	-25.5	-21.5	-4	1
6216	1914-01-03	CARIBOO LODGE	BC	1171393	-119.47	52.72	1096	-1.3	-1	-0.3	1
6217	1914-01-04	CARIBOO LODGE	BC	1171393	-119.47	52.72	1096	-2.9	-1	-1.9	1
6218	1914-01-05	CARIBOO LODGE	BC	1171393	-119.47	52.72	1096	-1.3	-1.1	-0.2	1
6219	1914-01-13	CARIBOO LODGE	BC	1171393	-119.47	52.72	1096	-2.3	-1.2	-1.1	1
6220	1914-01-17	CARIBOO LODGE	BC	1171393	-119.47	52.72	1096	-1.8	-1.1	-0.7	1
6221	1914-02-08	CARIBOO LODGE	BC	1171393	-119.47	52.72	1096	-17.5	-15.3	-2.2	1

6222	1914-02-09	CARIBOO LODGE	BC	1171393	-119.47	52.72	1096	-14.7	-14.2	-0.5	1
6223	1914-04-30	CARIBOO LODGE	BC	1171393	-119.47	52.72	1096	-0.2	0.1	-0.3	1
6224	1914-05-01	CARIBOO LODGE	BC	1171393	-119.47	52.72	1096	-1.3	-1	-0.3	1
6225	1914-10-20	CARIBOO LODGE	BC	1171393	-119.47	52.72	1096	0.4	2.4	-2	1
6226	1914-11-15	CARIBOO LODGE	BC	1171393	-119.47	52.72	1096	-2.9	-1.1	-1.8	1
6227	1914-11-23	CARIBOO LODGE	BC	1171393	-119.47	52.72	1096	-2.9	-2.3	-0.6	1
6228	1914-11-29	CARIBOO LODGE	BC	1171393	-119.47	52.72	1096	-7.7	-6.4	-1.3	1
6229	1914-12-02	CARIBOO LODGE	BC	1171393	-119.47	52.72	1096	-5.9	-4.8	-1.1	1
6230	1914-12-08	CARIBOO LODGE	BC	1171393	-119.47	52.72	1096	-3.5	-2.3	-1.2	1
6231	1914-12-18	CARIBOO LODGE	BC	1171393	-119.47	52.72	1096	-6.5	-4.8	-1.7	1
6232	1914-12-21	CARIBOO LODGE	BC	1171393	-119.47	52.72	1096	-1.3	-0.7	-0.6	1
6233	1914-12-28	CARIBOO LODGE	BC	1171393	-119.47	52.72	1096	-8.3	-7.7	-0.6	1
6234	1914-12-31	CARIBOO LODGE	BC	1171393	-119.47	52.72	1096	-15.3	-13.4	-1.9	1
6235	1916-01-05	CARIBOO LODGE	BC	1171393	-119.47	52.72	1096	-21.4	-20.3	-1.1	1
6236	1916-01-06	CARIBOO LODGE	BC	1171393	-119.47	52.72	1096	-15.3	-13.7	-1.6	1
6237	1916-01-09	CARIBOO LODGE	BC	1171393	-119.47	52.72	1096	-16.9	-16.7	-0.2	1
6238	1916-01-22	CARIBOO LODGE	BC	1171393	-119.47	52.72	1096	-23.6	-22.6	-1	1
6239	1916-01-23	CARIBOO LODGE	BC	1171393	-119.47	52.72	1096	-29.7	-25.7	-4	1
6240	1916-01-29	CARIBOO LODGE	BC	1171393	-119.47	52.72	1096	-27.5	-26.8	-0.7	1
6241	1916-02-13	CARIBOO LODGE	BC	1171393	-119.47	52.72	1096	-1.8	-0.8	-1	1
6242	1916-02-14	CARIBOO LODGE	BC	1171393	-119.47	52.72	1096	-1.8	-1	-0.8	1
6243	1916-02-15	CARIBOO LODGE	BC	1171393	-119.47	52.72	1096	1.7	2.4	-0.7	1
6244	1916-11-04	CARIBOO LODGE	BC	1171393	-119.47	52.72	1096	-1.3	-0.6	-0.7	1
6245	1916-11-08	CARIBOO LODGE	BC	1171393	-119.47	52.72	1096	-1.8	-0.8	-1	1
6246	1916-11-09	CARIBOO LODGE	BC	1171393	-119.47	52.72	1096	-1.3	-1.1	-0.2	1
6247	1916-11-21	CARIBOO LODGE	BC	1171393	-119.47	52.72	1096	-1.8	-0.8	-1	1
6248	1916-11-25	CARIBOO LODGE	BC	1171393	-119.47	52.72	1096	-5.9	-4.2	-1.7	1
6249	1916-12-01	CARIBOO LODGE	BC	1171393	-119.47	52.72	1096	-2.9	-1.1	-1.8	1
6250	1916-12-02	CARIBOO LODGE	BC	1171393	-119.47	52.72	1096	-4.1	-2.9	-1.2	1
6251	1916-12-03	CARIBOO LODGE	BC	1171393	-119.47	52.72	1096	-1.2	-1.1	-0.1	1
6252	1916-12-08	CARIBOO LODGE	BC	1171393	-119.47	52.72	1096	-11.3	-9.1	-2.2	1
6253	1916-12-18	CARIBOO LODGE	BC	1171393	-119.47	52.72	1096	-9	-6.4	-2.6	1
6254	1916-12-30	CARIBOO LODGE	BC	1171393	-119.47	52.72	1096	-14.1	-13.4	-0.7	1
6255	1916-12-31	CARIBOO LODGE	BC	1171393	-119.47	52.72	1096	-11.3	-11.2	-0.1	1

6256	1917-01-01	CARIBOO LODGE	BC	1171393	-119.47	52.72	1096	-8.3	-6.9	-1.4	1
6257	1917-01-02	CARIBOO LODGE	BC	1171393	-119.47	52.72	1096	-7.7	-4.8	-2.9	1
6258	1917-01-25	CARIBOO LODGE	BC	1171393	-119.47	52.72	1096	-4.1	-2.9	-1.2	1
6259	1917-01-29	CARIBOO LODGE	BC	1171393	-119.47	52.72	1096	-25.8	-24.7	-1.1	1
6260	1917-02-05	CARIBOO LODGE	BC	1171393	-119.47	52.72	1096	-2.3	-1.4	-0.9	1
6261	1917-02-21	CARIBOO LODGE	BC	1171393	-119.47	52.72	1096	-20.3	-19	-1.3	1
6262	1917-10-29	CARIBOO LODGE	BC	1171393	-119.47	52.72	1096	-3.5	-2.3	-1.2	1
6263	1917-11-27	CARIBOO LODGE	BC	1171393	-119.47	52.72	1096	-1.2	-0.8	-0.4	1
6264	1917-12-03	CARIBOO LODGE	BC	1171393	-119.47	52.72	1096	-15.8	-15.1	-0.7	1
6265	1917-12-08	CARIBOO LODGE	BC	1171393	-119.47	52.72	1096	-9	-7.6	-1.4	1
6266	1917-12-13	CARIBOO LODGE	BC	1171393	-119.47	52.72	1096	-21.4	-17	-4.4	1
6267	1917-12-15	CARIBOO LODGE	BC	1171393	-119.47	52.72	1096	-9.5	-6.9	-2.6	1
6268	1917-12-27	CARIBOO LODGE	BC	1171393	-119.47	52.72	1096	-25.3	-19.7	-5.6	1
6269	1917-12-30	CARIBOO LODGE	BC	1171393	-119.47	52.72	1096	-8.3	-7.6	-0.7	1
6270	1918-01-02	CARIBOO LODGE	BC	1171393	-119.47	52.72	1096	1.7	2.3	-0.6	1
6271	1918-01-12	CARIBOO LODGE	BC	1171393	-119.47	52.72	1096	-11.3	-11.2	-0.1	1
6272	1918-02-03	CARIBOO LODGE	BC	1171393	-119.47	52.72	1096	-10.1	-7.6	-2.5	1
6273	1918-02-28	CARIBOO LODGE	BC	1171393	-119.47	52.72	1096	-4.7	-4.2	-0.5	1
6274	1918-11-13	CARIBOO LODGE	BC	1171393	-119.47	52.72	1096	-0.2	0.1	-0.3	1
6275	1918-11-18	CARIBOO LODGE	BC	1171393	-119.47	52.72	1096	0.4	0.8	-0.4	1
6276	1918-11-20	CARIBOO LODGE	BC	1171393	-119.47	52.72	1096	-1.2	-0.9	-0.3	1
6277	1918-11-26	CARIBOO LODGE	BC	1171393	-119.47	52.72	1096	-7.7	-5.8	-1.9	1
6278	1918-11-30	CARIBOO LODGE	BC	1171393	-119.47	52.72	1096	-2.3	-1	-1.3	1
6279	1918-12-07	CARIBOO LODGE	BC	1171393	-119.47	52.72	1096	-0.2	0.1	-0.3	1
6280	1918-12-08	CARIBOO LODGE	BC	1171393	-119.47	52.72	1096	0.4	0.8	-0.4	1
6281	1918-12-13	CARIBOO LODGE	BC	1171393	-119.47	52.72	1096	-7.1	-6.9	-0.2	1
6282	1918-12-18	CARIBOO LODGE	BC	1171393	-119.47	52.72	1096	-5.2	-4.8	-0.4	1
6283	1918-12-23	CARIBOO LODGE	BC	1171393	-119.47	52.72	1096	-10.7	-9.7	-1	1
6284	1918-12-27	CARIBOO LODGE	BC	1171393	-119.47	52.72	1096	-8.3	-8.2	-0.1	1
6285	1918-12-28	CARIBOO LODGE	BC	1171393	-119.47	52.72	1096	-6	-4.8	-1.2	1
6286	1919-01-02	CARIBOO LODGE	BC	1171393	-119.47	52.72	1096	-15.3	-14.5	-0.8	1
6287	1919-01-13	CARIBOO LODGE	BC	1171393	-119.47	52.72	1096	-2.3	-0.9	-1.4	1
6288	1919-01-14	CARIBOO LODGE	BC	1171393	-119.47	52.72	1096	-1.2	-0.6	-0.6	1
6289	1919-01-15	CARIBOO LODGE	BC	1171393	-119.47	52.72	1096	-1.8	-1	-0.8	1

6290	1919-01-23	CARIBOO LODGE	BC	1171393	-119.47	52.72	1096	-1.8	-1.4	-0.4	1
6291	1919-01-26	CARIBOO LODGE	BC	1171393	-119.47	52.72	1096	-3.5	-3	-0.5	1
6292	1919-02-09	CARIBOO LODGE	BC	1171393	-119.47	52.72	1096	-5.3	-4.2	-1.1	1
6293	1919-03-02	CARIBOO LODGE	BC	1171393	-119.47	52.72	1096	-20.8	-20.2	-0.6	1
6294	1919-03-11	CARIBOO LODGE	BC	1171393	-119.47	52.72	1096	-1.8	-1	-0.8	1
6295	1919-10-11	CARIBOO LODGE	BC	1171393	-119.47	52.72	1096	-2.3	-1.1	-1.2	1
6296	1919-10-28	CARIBOO LODGE	BC	1171393	-119.47	52.72	1096	-1.8	-1.4	-0.4	1
6297	1919-10-31	CARIBOO LODGE	BC	1171393	-119.47	52.72	1096	-2.3	-2.2	-0.1	1
6298	1919-11-02	CARIBOO LODGE	BC	1171393	-119.47	52.72	1096	-4.1	-3.7	-0.4	1
6299	1919-11-14	CARIBOO LODGE	BC	1171393	-119.47	52.72	1096	-4.7	-4.2	-0.5	1
6300	1919-11-15	CARIBOO LODGE	BC	1171393	-119.47	52.72	1096	-3.5	-1.1	-2.4	1
6301	1919-11-21	CARIBOO LODGE	BC	1171393	-119.47	52.72	1096	-1.2	-0.6	-0.6	1
6302	1919-11-28	CARIBOO LODGE	BC	1171393	-119.47	52.72	1096	-10.7	-9.7	-1	1
6303	1919-12-15	CARIBOO LODGE	BC	1171393	-119.47	52.72	1096	-11.3	-9.7	-1.6	1
6304	1919-12-16	CARIBOO LODGE	BC	1171393	-119.47	52.72	1096	-10.7	-9.7	-1	1
6305	1919-12-18	CARIBOO LODGE	BC	1171393	-119.47	52.72	1096	-3.5	-3	-0.5	1
6306	1919-12-23	CARIBOO LODGE	BC	1171393	-119.47	52.72	1096	1.7	2.7	-1	1
6307	1919-12-26	CARIBOO LODGE	BC	1171393	-119.47	52.72	1096	-0.2	0.8	-1	1
6308	1920-01-11	CARIBOO LODGE	BC	1171393	-119.47	52.72	1096	-9	-7.7	-1.3	1
6309	1920-01-12	CARIBOO LODGE	BC	1171393	-119.47	52.72	1096	-8.3	-6.4	-1.9	1
6310	1920-01-14	CARIBOO LODGE	BC	1171393	-119.47	52.72	1096	-0.2	0.1	-0.3	1
6311	1920-02-05	CARIBOO LODGE	BC	1171393	-119.47	52.72	1096	-1.2	-0.6	-0.6	1
6312	1920-10-06	CARIBOO LODGE	BC	1171393	-119.47	52.72	1096	3.6	4.3	-0.7	1
6313	1920-11-15	CARIBOO LODGE	BC	1171393	-119.47	52.72	1096	-1.2	-0.7	-0.5	1
6314	1920-12-01	CARIBOO LODGE	BC	1171393	-119.47	52.72	1096	-0.8	-0.6	-0.2	1
6315	1920-12-06	CARIBOO LODGE	BC	1171393	-119.47	52.72	1096	-2.9	-1.1	-1.8	1
6316	1920-12-11	CARIBOO LODGE	BC	1171393	-119.47	52.72	1096	-3.5	-2.9	-0.6	1
6317	1920-12-24	CARIBOO LODGE	BC	1171393	-119.47	52.72	1096	-9.5	-9	-0.5	1
6318	1921-01-12	CARIBOO LODGE	BC	1171393	-119.47	52.72	1096	-9.5	-7.6	-1.9	1
6319	1921-01-14	CARIBOO LODGE	BC	1171393	-119.47	52.72	1096	-4	-1.4	-2.6	1
6320	1921-02-23	CARIBOO LODGE	BC	1171393	-119.47	52.72	1096	-1.8	-1.4	-0.4	1
6321	1922-01-14	CARIBOO LODGE	BC	1171393	-119.47	52.72	1096	-10.1	-9	-1.1	1
6322	1922-01-20	CARIBOO LODGE	BC	1171393	-119.47	52.72	1096	-14.7	-13.3	-1.4	1
6323	1922-02-08	CARIBOO LODGE	BC	1171393	-119.47	52.72	1096	-19.7	-18.1	-1.6	1

6324	1922-02-16	CARIBOO LODGE	BC	1171393	-119.47	52.72	1096	-7.1	-5.3	-1.8	1
6325	1922-11-17	CARIBOO LODGE	BC	1171393	-119.47	52.72	1096	-1.2	-1.1	-0.1	1
6326	1922-12-09	CARIBOO LODGE	BC	1171393	-119.47	52.72	1096	-20.8	-20.3	-0.5	1
6327	1922-12-10	CARIBOO LODGE	BC	1171393	-119.47	52.72	1096	-24.2	-19.8	-4.4	1
6328	1922-12-15	CARIBOO LODGE	BC	1171393	-119.47	52.72	1096	-23	-20.3	-2.7	1
6329	1922-12-16	CARIBOO LODGE	BC	1171393	-119.47	52.72	1096	-21.9	-21.7	-0.2	1
6330	1922-12-26	CARIBOO LODGE	BC	1171393	-119.47	52.72	1096	-1.2	-0.8	-0.4	1
6331	1923-02-12	CARIBOO LODGE	BC	1171393	-119.47	52.72	1096	-24.2	-22.6	-1.6	1
6332	1923-03-06	CARIBOO LODGE	BC	1171393	-119.47	52.72	1096	-1.3	-1.1	-0.2	1
6333	1923-03-11	CARIBOO LODGE	BC	1171393	-119.47	52.72	1096	-2.9	-2.2	-0.7	1
6334	1923-11-23	CARIBOO LODGE	BC	1171393	-119.47	52.72	1096	-1.3	-0.9	-0.4	1
6335	1923-11-26	CARIBOO LODGE	BC	1171393	-119.47	52.72	1096	-2.3	-1.4	-0.9	1
6336	1923-11-27	CARIBOO LODGE	BC	1171393	-119.47	52.72	1096	-2.9	-1.1	-1.8	1
6337	1923-12-04	CARIBOO LODGE	BC	1171393	-119.47	52.72	1096	-0.2	0.9	-1.1	1
6338	1923-12-06	CARIBOO LODGE	BC	1171393	-119.47	52.72	1096	-3.5	-3	-0.5	1
6339	1923-12-10	CARIBOO LODGE	BC	1171393	-119.47	52.72	1096	-3.5	-1.4	-2.1	1
6340	1923-12-15	CARIBOO LODGE	BC	1171393	-119.47	52.72	1096	-1.3	-0.9	-0.4	1
6341	1923-12-17	CARIBOO LODGE	BC	1171393	-119.47	52.72	1096	1.8	1.9	-0.1	1
6342	1923-12-30	CARIBOO LODGE	BC	1171393	-119.47	52.72	1096	-27.5	-26.8	-0.7	1
6343	1924-01-06	CARIBOO LODGE	BC	1171393	-119.47	52.72	1096	-9.5	-8.3	-1.2	1
6344	1924-02-12	CARIBOO LODGE	BC	1171393	-119.47	52.72	1096	-0.2	0.2	-0.4	1
6345	1924-02-13	CARIBOO LODGE	BC	1171393	-119.47	52.72	1096	-4.1	-2.9	-1.2	1
6346	1924-02-14	CARIBOO LODGE	BC	1171393	-119.47	52.72	1096	-7.2	-6.4	-0.8	1
6347	1924-02-17	CARIBOO LODGE	BC	1171393	-119.47	52.72	1096	-8.3	-7.6	-0.7	1
6348	1924-11-02	CARIBOO LODGE	BC	1171393	-119.47	52.72	1096	-1.3	-0.6	-0.7	1
6349	1924-11-07	CARIBOO LODGE	BC	1171393	-119.47	52.72	1096	-7.1	-6.4	-0.7	1
6350	1924-11-18	CARIBOO LODGE	BC	1171393	-119.47	52.72	1096	-1.3	-0.7	-0.6	1
6351	1924-11-28	CARIBOO LODGE	BC	1171393	-119.47	52.72	1096	-3.5	-2.1	-1.4	1
6352	1924-11-30	CARIBOO LODGE	BC	1171393	-119.47	52.72	1096	-2.3	-2.1	-0.2	1
6353	1924-12-04	CARIBOO LODGE	BC	1171393	-119.47	52.72	1096	-1.8	-1.4	-0.4	1
6354	1924-12-13	CARIBOO LODGE	BC	1171393	-119.47	52.72	1096	-4	-1.4	-2.6	1
6355	1924-12-15	CARIBOO LODGE	BC	1171393	-119.47	52.72	1096	-27.5	-24.1	-3.4	1
6356	1924-12-19	CARIBOO LODGE	BC	1171393	-119.47	52.72	1096	-24.7	-23.1	-1.6	1
6357	1925-01-05	CARIBOO LODGE	BC	1171393	-119.47	52.72	1096	-5.3	-3.7	-1.6	1

6358	1925-01-16	CARIBOO LODGE	BC	1171393	-119.47	52.72	1096	-7.7	-5.8	-1.9	1
6359	1925-01-17	CARIBOO LODGE	BC	1171393	-119.47	52.72	1096	-6.5	-5.3	-1.2	1
6360	1925-01-26	CARIBOO LODGE	BC	1171393	-119.47	52.72	1096	-9	-8.3	-0.7	1
6361	1925-01-31	CARIBOO LODGE	BC	1171393	-119.47	52.72	1096	-19.7	-19	-0.7	1
6362	1925-11-03	CARIBOO LODGE	BC	1171393	-119.47	52.72	1096	-5.9	-5.3	-0.6	1
6363	1925-11-23	CARIBOO LODGE	BC	1171393	-119.47	52.72	1096	-2.3	-1.1	-1.2	1
6364	1925-11-24	CARIBOO LODGE	BC	1171393	-119.47	52.72	1096	-1.8	-1.4	-0.4	1
6365	1925-12-01	CARIBOO LODGE	BC	1171393	-119.47	52.72	1096	-0.8	-0.6	-0.2	1
6366	1925-12-09	CARIBOO LODGE	BC	1171393	-119.47	52.72	1096	0.4	0.9	-0.5	1
6367	1925-12-10	CARIBOO LODGE	BC	1171393	-119.47	52.72	1096	-0.8	0	-0.8	1
6368	1925-12-13	CARIBOO LODGE	BC	1171393	-119.47	52.72	1096	-6.5	-5.3	-1.2	1
6369	1925-12-16	CARIBOO LODGE	BC	1171393	-119.47	52.72	1096	-0.1	0.9	-1	1
6370	1925-12-17	CARIBOO LODGE	BC	1171393	-119.47	52.72	1096	0.4	0.9	-0.5	1
6371	1925-12-18	CARIBOO LODGE	BC	1171393	-119.47	52.72	1096	-0.8	0	-0.8	1
6372	1925-12-23	CARIBOO LODGE	BC	1171393	-119.47	52.72	1096	-2.9	-1	-1.9	1
6373	1925-12-24	CARIBOO LODGE	BC	1171393	-119.47	52.72	1096	-1.8	-1.1	-0.7	1
6374	1925-12-30	CARIBOO LODGE	BC	1171393	-119.47	52.72	1096	-5.9	-5.8	-0.1	1
6375	1925-12-31	CARIBOO LODGE	BC	1171393	-119.47	52.72	1096	-7.2	-6.4	-0.8	1
6376	1926-01-01	CARIBOO LODGE	BC	1171393	-119.47	52.72	1096	-7.2	-5.8	-1.4	1
6377	1926-01-02	CARIBOO LODGE	BC	1171393	-119.47	52.72	1096	-7.2	-6.4	-0.8	1
6378	1926-01-05	CARIBOO LODGE	BC	1171393	-119.47	52.72	1096	-6.5	-5.8	-0.7	1
6379	1926-01-11	CARIBOO LODGE	BC	1171393	-119.47	52.72	1096	-6.5	-6.4	-0.1	1
6380	1926-01-16	CARIBOO LODGE	BC	1171393	-119.47	52.72	1096	-3.5	-1.4	-2.1	1
6381	1926-01-17	CARIBOO LODGE	BC	1171393	-119.47	52.72	1096	-2.9	-1.4	-1.5	1
6382	1926-01-18	CARIBOO LODGE	BC	1171393	-119.47	52.72	1096	-5.9	-5.8	-0.1	1
6383	1926-01-28	CARIBOO LODGE	BC	1171393	-119.47	52.72	1096	-4.1	-3	-1.1	1
6384	1926-02-07	CARIBOO LODGE	BC	1171393	-119.47	52.72	1096	-0.8	-0.6	-0.2	1
6385	1926-02-09	CARIBOO LODGE	BC	1171393	-119.47	52.72	1096	0.5	2	-1.5	1
6386	1926-09-21	CARIBOO LODGE	BC	1171393	-119.47	52.72	1096	-2.3	-1.4	-0.9	1
6387	1926-11-11	CARIBOO LODGE	BC	1171393	-119.47	52.72	1096	3.1	3.2	-0.1	1
6388	1926-11-17	CARIBOO LODGE	BC	1171393	-119.47	52.72	1096	-2.3	-0.7	-1.6	1
6389	1926-11-23	CARIBOO LODGE	BC	1171393	-119.47	52.72	1096	-4.7	-3.7	-1	1
6390	1926-11-24	CARIBOO LODGE	BC	1171393	-119.47	52.72	1096	-5.9	-5.8	-0.1	1
6391	1926-11-27	CARIBOO LODGE	BC	1171393	-119.47	52.72	1096	-7.7	-7.6	-0.1	1

6392	1926-11-29	CARIBOO LODGE	BC	1171393	-119.47	52.72	1096	-9	-6.4	-2.6	1
6393	1926-12-10	CARIBOO LODGE	BC	1171393	-119.47	52.72	1096	-2.3	-2.2	-0.1	1
6394	1926-12-15	CARIBOO LODGE	BC	1171393	-119.47	52.72	1096	-18	-17.8	-0.2	1
6395	1926-12-28	CARIBOO LODGE	BC	1171393	-119.47	52.72	1096	-3.5	-3	-0.5	1
6396	1926-12-29	CARIBOO LODGE	BC	1171393	-119.47	52.72	1096	-1.2	-0.8	-0.4	1
6397	1927-01-08	CARIBOO LODGE	BC	1171393	-119.47	52.72	1096	-7.2	-6.9	-0.3	1
6398	1927-01-15	CARIBOO LODGE	BC	1171393	-119.47	52.72	1096	-9	-7.6	-1.4	1
6399	1927-01-17	CARIBOO LODGE	BC	1171393	-119.47	52.72	1096	-16.4	-15.2	-1.2	1
6400	1927-01-22	CARIBOO LODGE	BC	1171393	-119.47	52.72	1096	-16.9	-15.8	-1.1	1
6401	1927-01-26	CARIBOO LODGE	BC	1171393	-119.47	52.72	1096	-4	-3.7	-0.3	1
6402	1927-01-27	CARIBOO LODGE	BC	1171393	-119.47	52.72	1096	-2.9	-2.2	-0.7	1
6403	1927-02-03	CARIBOO LODGE	BC	1171393	-119.47	52.72	1096	-1.3	-0.9	-0.4	1
6404	1927-02-15	CARIBOO LODGE	BC	1171393	-119.47	52.72	1096	-18	-16.7	-1.3	1
6405	1927-02-25	CARIBOO LODGE	BC	1171393	-119.47	52.72	1096	-2.3	-2.1	-0.2	1
6406	1927-03-07	CARIBOO LODGE	BC	1171393	-119.47	52.72	1096	-2.3	-1	-1.3	1
6407	1927-12-02	CARIBOO LODGE	BC	1171393	-119.47	52.72	1096	-1.8	-1.4	-0.4	1
6408	1927-12-18	CARIBOO LODGE	BC	1171393	-119.47	52.72	1096	-9	-8.2	-0.8	1
6409	1927-12-26	CARIBOO LODGE	BC	1171393	-119.47	52.72	1096	-4	-3.7	-0.3	1
6410	1927-12-27	CARIBOO LODGE	BC	1171393	-119.47	52.72	1096	-6.5	-6.4	-0.1	1
6411	1928-01-05	CARIBOO LODGE	BC	1171393	-119.47	52.72	1096	-2.9	-2.2	-0.7	1
6412	1928-01-13	CARIBOO LODGE	BC	1171393	-119.47	52.72	1096	-4.7	-3.7	-1	1
6413	1928-01-18	CARIBOO LODGE	BC	1171393	-119.47	52.72	1096	-9.5	-9	-0.5	1
6414	1928-01-28	CARIBOO LODGE	BC	1171393	-119.47	52.72	1096	-4	-2.8	-1.2	1
6415	1928-02-11	CARIBOO LODGE	BC	1171393	-119.47	52.72	1096	-1.3	-1.1	-0.2	1
6416	1928-12-03	CARIBOO LODGE	BC	1171393	-119.47	52.72	1096	-18	-17.4	-0.6	1
6417	1928-12-04	CARIBOO LODGE	BC	1171393	-119.47	52.72	1096	-13.5	-11.2	-2.3	1
6418	1928-12-05	CARIBOO LODGE	BC	1171393	-119.47	52.72	1096	-11.3	-10.5	-0.8	1
6419	1928-12-06	CARIBOO LODGE	BC	1171393	-119.47	52.72	1096	-6.5	-6.4	-0.1	1
6420	1928-12-07	CARIBOO LODGE	BC	1171393	-119.47	52.72	1096	-2.9	-0.6	-2.3	1
6421	1928-12-08	CARIBOO LODGE	BC	1171393	-119.47	52.72	1096	-2.3	0	-2.3	1
6422	1928-12-09	CARIBOO LODGE	BC	1171393	-119.47	52.72	1096	-2.3	0	-2.3	1
6423	1928-12-10	CARIBOO LODGE	BC	1171393	-119.47	52.72	1096	-2.3	-0.9	-1.4	1
6424	1928-12-11	CARIBOO LODGE	BC	1171393	-119.47	52.72	1096	-3.5	-0.9	-2.6	1
6425	1928-12-14	CARIBOO LODGE	BC	1171393	-119.47	52.72	1096	-15.8	-15.2	-0.6	1

6426	1928-12-16	CARIBOO LODGE	BC	1171393	-119.47	52.72	1096	-8.3	-7.6	-0.7	1
6427	1928-12-17	CARIBOO LODGE	BC	1171393	-119.47	52.72	1096	-10.1	-9	-1.1	1
6428	1928-12-18	CARIBOO LODGE	BC	1171393	-119.47	52.72	1096	-8.3	-7.7	-0.6	1
6429	1928-12-19	CARIBOO LODGE	BC	1171393	-119.47	52.72	1096	-8.3	-7	-1.3	1
6430	1928-12-20	CARIBOO LODGE	BC	1171393	-119.47	52.72	1096	-5.9	-4.8	-1.1	1
6431	1928-12-21	CARIBOO LODGE	BC	1171393	-119.47	52.72	1096	-5.9	-3.6	-2.3	1
6432	1929-01-05	CARIBOO LODGE	BC	1171393	-119.47	52.72	1096	-9	-6.4	-2.6	1
6433	1929-01-06	CARIBOO LODGE	BC	1171393	-119.47	52.72	1096	-6.5	-5.8	-0.7	1
6434	1929-01-07	CARIBOO LODGE	BC	1171393	-119.47	52.72	1096	-5.3	-2.9	-2.4	1
6435	1929-01-08	CARIBOO LODGE	BC	1171393	-119.47	52.72	1096	-5.3	-1.4	-3.9	1
6436	1929-01-10	CARIBOO LODGE	BC	1171393	-119.47	52.72	1096	-3.5	-1.4	-2.1	1
6437	1929-01-13	CARIBOO LODGE	BC	1171393	-119.47	52.72	1096	-4	-3.6	-0.4	1
6438	1929-01-20	CARIBOO LODGE	BC	1171393	-119.47	52.72	1096	-12.4	-11.2	-1.2	1
6439	1929-01-24	CARIBOO LODGE	BC	1171393	-119.47	52.72	1096	-18	-14.8	-3.2	1
6440	1929-01-31	CARIBOO LODGE	BC	1171393	-119.47	52.72	1096	-18.6	-17.8	-0.8	1
6441	1929-02-11	CARIBOO LODGE	BC	1171393	-119.47	52.72	1096	-2.9	-1.1	-1.8	1
6442	1929-02-15	CARIBOO LODGE	BC	1171393	-119.47	52.72	1096	-4.1	-1.1	-3	1
6443	1929-03-03	CARIBOO LODGE	BC	1171393	-119.47	52.72	1096	0.4	0.7	-0.3	1
6444	1929-04-05	CARIBOO LODGE	BC	1171393	-119.47	52.72	1096	-9.5	-6.4	-3.1	1
6445	1929-11-12	CARIBOO LODGE	BC	1171393	-119.47	52.72	1096	-0.2	0.9	-1.1	1
6446	1929-11-19	CARIBOO LODGE	BC	1171393	-119.47	52.72	1096	-7.2	-5.8	-1.4	1
6447	1929-11-21	CARIBOO LODGE	BC	1171393	-119.47	52.72	1096	-7.2	-6.4	-0.8	1
6448	1929-11-26	CARIBOO LODGE	BC	1171393	-119.47	52.72	1096	-0.8	-0.6	-0.2	1
6449	1929-11-27	CARIBOO LODGE	BC	1171393	-119.47	52.72	1096	-1.2	-0.7	-0.5	1
6450	1929-11-28	CARIBOO LODGE	BC	1171393	-119.47	52.72	1096	-1.8	-0.8	-1	1
6451	1929-12-11	CARIBOO LODGE	BC	1171393	-119.47	52.72	1096	-24.7	-21.1	-3.6	1
6452	1929-12-13	CARIBOO LODGE	BC	1171393	-119.47	52.72	1096	-21.4	-17.1	-4.3	1
6453	1929-12-21	CARIBOO LODGE	BC	1171393	-119.47	52.72	1096	-7.7	-5.3	-2.4	1
6454	1929-12-23	CARIBOO LODGE	BC	1171393	-119.47	52.72	1096	-2.9	-1.1	-1.8	1
6455	1929-12-24	CARIBOO LODGE	BC	1171393	-119.47	52.72	1096	-1.2	0	-1.2	1
6456	1929-12-27	CARIBOO LODGE	BC	1171393	-119.47	52.72	1096	-2.9	-2.1	-0.8	1
6457	1929-12-28	CARIBOO LODGE	BC	1171393	-119.47	52.72	1096	-2.9	-1.1	-1.8	1
6458	1930-01-06	CARIBOO LODGE	BC	1171393	-119.47	52.72	1096	-34.2	-33.4	-0.8	1
6459	1930-01-28	CARIBOO LODGE	BC	1171393	-119.47	52.72	1096	-14.1	-12.8	-1.3	1

6460	1930-01-29	CARIBOO LODGE	BC	1171393	-119.47	52.72	1096	-7.7	-6.9	-0.8	1
6461	1930-01-30	CARIBOO LODGE	BC	1171393	-119.47	52.72	1096	-6.5	-4.2	-2.3	1
6462	1930-01-31	CARIBOO LODGE	BC	1171393	-119.47	52.72	1096	-2.9	-1.1	-1.8	1
6463	1930-02-01	CARIBOO LODGE	BC	1171393	-119.47	52.72	1096	-0.1	0.1	-0.2	1
6464	1930-02-03	CARIBOO LODGE	BC	1171393	-119.47	52.72	1096	-4.1	-1.4	-2.7	1
6465	1930-02-04	CARIBOO LODGE	BC	1171393	-119.47	52.72	1096	-2.3	-1.4	-0.9	1
6466	1930-02-14	CARIBOO LODGE	BC	1171393	-119.47	52.72	1096	-7.2	-5.3	-1.9	1
6467	1930-02-15	CARIBOO LODGE	BC	1171393	-119.47	52.72	1096	-1.2	-0.8	-0.4	1
6468	1930-03-20	CARIBOO LODGE	BC	1171393	-119.47	52.72	1096	-4.1	-2.1	-2	1
6469	1930-03-21	CARIBOO LODGE	BC	1171393	-119.47	52.72	1096	-2.9	-1	-1.9	1
6470	1930-09-26	CARIBOO LODGE	BC	1171393	-119.47	52.72	1096	6.1	6.4	-0.3	1
6471	1930-10-05	CARIBOO LODGE	BC	1171393	-119.47	52.72	1096	1.8	2.7	-0.9	1
6472	1930-11-19	CARIBOO LODGE	BC	1171393	-119.47	52.72	1096	-4.1	-3.7	-0.4	1
6473	1930-11-23	CARIBOO LODGE	BC	1171393	-119.47	52.72	1096	-4.1	-2.3	-1.8	1
6474	1930-11-29	CARIBOO LODGE	BC	1171393	-119.47	52.72	1096	-2.9	-1.4	-1.5	1
6475	1930-11-30	CARIBOO LODGE	BC	1171393	-119.47	52.72	1096	-1.8	-0.6	-1.2	1
6476	1930-12-01	CARIBOO LODGE	BC	1171393	-119.47	52.72	1096	-1.8	-0.8	-1	1
6477	1930-12-07	CARIBOO LODGE	BC	1171393	-119.47	52.72	1096	-0.8	0.2	-1	1
6478	1930-12-10	CARIBOO LODGE	BC	1171393	-119.47	52.72	1096	-0.8	-0.6	-0.2	1
6479	1930-12-14	CARIBOO LODGE	BC	1171393	-119.47	52.72	1096	-1.2	-0.6	-0.6	1
6480	1930-12-18	CARIBOO LODGE	BC	1171393	-119.47	52.72	1096	-4.1	-3	-1.1	1
6481	1930-12-21	CARIBOO LODGE	BC	1171393	-119.47	52.72	1096	-3.5	-1.4	-2.1	1
6482	1930-12-22	CARIBOO LODGE	BC	1171393	-119.47	52.72	1096	-3.5	-1.4	-2.1	1
6483	1930-12-24	CARIBOO LODGE	BC	1171393	-119.47	52.72	1096	-2.9	-2.3	-0.6	1
6484	1930-12-30	CARIBOO LODGE	BC	1171393	-119.47	52.72	1096	-6.5	-5.3	-1.2	1
6485	1930-12-31	CARIBOO LODGE	BC	1171393	-119.47	52.72	1096	-6.5	-4.2	-2.3	1
6486	1931-01-01	CARIBOO LODGE	BC	1171393	-119.47	52.72	1096	-4.1	-3	-1.1	1
6487	1931-01-04	CARIBOO LODGE	BC	1171393	-119.47	52.72	1096	-1.8	-0.8	-1	1
6488	1931-01-09	CARIBOO LODGE	BC	1171393	-119.47	52.72	1096	-6	-5.3	-0.7	1
6489	1931-01-12	CARIBOO LODGE	BC	1171393	-119.47	52.72	1096	-5.3	-4.2	-1.1	1
6490	1931-01-13	CARIBOO LODGE	BC	1171393	-119.47	52.72	1096	-5.3	-2.3	-3	1
6491	1931-01-21	CARIBOO LODGE	BC	1171393	-119.47	52.72	1096	-2.9	-2.3	-0.6	1
6492	1931-01-22	CARIBOO LODGE	BC	1171393	-119.47	52.72	1096	-3.5	-0.9	-2.6	1
6493	1931-01-24	CARIBOO LODGE	BC	1171393	-119.47	52.72	1096	-1.2	-0.6	-0.6	1

6494	1931-01-25	CARIBOO LODGE	BC	1171393	-119.47	52.72	1096	-1.8	-1.1	-0.7	1
6495	1931-01-26	CARIBOO LODGE	BC	1171393	-119.47	52.72	1096	-0.1	0.2	-0.3	1
6496	1931-01-27	CARIBOO LODGE	BC	1171393	-119.47	52.72	1096	1.1	2.8	-1.7	1
6497	1931-02-17	CARIBOO LODGE	BC	1171393	-119.47	52.72	1096	3.1	3.2	-0.1	1
6498	1931-02-25	CARIBOO LODGE	BC	1171393	-119.47	52.72	1096	-1.2	-1.1	-0.1	1
6499	1931-05-06	CARIBOO LODGE	BC	1171393	-119.47	52.72	1096	-0.2	1.5	-1.7	1
6500	1931-10-24	CARIBOO LODGE	BC	1171393	-119.47	52.72	1096	1.8	3.3	-1.5	1
6501	1931-11-11	CARIBOO LODGE	BC	1171393	-119.47	52.72	1096	-1.8	-0.9	-0.9	1
6502	1931-11-12	CARIBOO LODGE	BC	1171393	-119.47	52.72	1096	-2.3	-1.4	-0.9	1
6503	1931-11-18	CARIBOO LODGE	BC	1171393	-119.47	52.72	1096	-11.8	-8.3	-3.5	1
6504	1931-12-01	CARIBOO LODGE	BC	1171393	-119.47	52.72	1096	-7.1	-5.3	-1.8	1
6505	1931-12-02	CARIBOO LODGE	BC	1171393	-119.47	52.72	1096	-6	-5.8	-0.2	1
6506	1931-12-14	CARIBOO LODGE	BC	1171393	-119.47	52.72	1096	-8.3	-6.4	-1.9	1
6507	1931-12-15	CARIBOO LODGE	BC	1171393	-119.47	52.72	1096	-7.7	-4.8	-2.9	1
6508	1931-12-16	CARIBOO LODGE	BC	1171393	-119.47	52.72	1096	-5.3	-3.7	-1.6	1
6509	1931-12-17	CARIBOO LODGE	BC	1171393	-119.47	52.72	1096	-1.3	1.5	-2.8	1
6510	1931-12-18	CARIBOO LODGE	BC	1171393	-119.47	52.72	1096	-0.2	1.5	-1.7	1
6511	1931-12-21	CARIBOO LODGE	BC	1171393	-119.47	52.72	1096	-8.3	-6.4	-1.9	1
6512	1931-12-23	CARIBOO LODGE	BC	1171393	-119.47	52.72	1096	-4.7	-1.4	-3.3	1
6513	1931-12-31	CARIBOO LODGE	BC	1171393	-119.47	52.72	1096	-6.5	-4.8	-1.7	1
6514	1932-01-06	CARIBOO LODGE	BC	1171393	-119.47	52.72	1096	-4.7	-4.2	-0.5	1
6515	1932-01-07	CARIBOO LODGE	BC	1171393	-119.47	52.72	1096	-1.3	-0.6	-0.7	1
6516	1932-01-15	CARIBOO LODGE	BC	1171393	-119.47	52.72	1096	-15.8	-15.1	-0.7	1
6517	1932-01-17	CARIBOO LODGE	BC	1171393	-119.47	52.72	1096	-9.5	-7.7	-1.8	1
6518	1932-01-24	CARIBOO LODGE	BC	1171393	-119.47	52.72	1096	-6.5	-4.2	-2.3	1
6519	1932-02-22	CARIBOO LODGE	BC	1171393	-119.47	52.72	1096	-0.8	1.9	-2.7	1
6520	1932-11-01	CARIBOO LODGE	BC	1171393	-119.47	52.72	1096	-0.8	0.1	-0.9	1
6521	1932-11-04	CARIBOO LODGE	BC	1171393	-119.47	52.72	1096	0.4	1.5	-1.1	1
6522	1932-11-11	CARIBOO LODGE	BC	1171393	-119.47	52.72	1096	-2.9	-1.4	-1.5	1
6523	1932-11-16	CARIBOO LODGE	BC	1171393	-119.47	52.72	1096	-2.3	-0.6	-1.7	1
6524	1932-11-17	CARIBOO LODGE	BC	1171393	-119.47	52.72	1096	-0.8	0.1	-0.9	1
6525	1932-11-20	CARIBOO LODGE	BC	1171393	-119.47	52.72	1096	-2.3	-1.4	-0.9	1
6526	1932-11-22	CARIBOO LODGE	BC	1171393	-119.47	52.72	1096	-1.2	0.1	-1.3	1
6527	1932-11-25	CARIBOO LODGE	BC	1171393	-119.47	52.72	1096	-2.9	-1.1	-1.8	1

6528	1932-11-26	CARIBOO LODGE	BC	1171393	-119.47	52.72	1096	-0.8	1.9	-2.7	1
6529	1932-12-02	CARIBOO LODGE	BC	1171393	-119.47	52.72	1096	-1.8	-1.2	-0.6	1
6530	1932-12-06	CARIBOO LODGE	BC	1171393	-119.47	52.72	1096	-21.4	-17	-4.4	1
6531	1932-12-11	CARIBOO LODGE	BC	1171393	-119.47	52.72	1096	-17.5	-15	-2.5	1
6532	1932-12-16	CARIBOO LODGE	BC	1171393	-119.47	52.72	1096	-15.3	-15.2	-0.1	1
6533	1932-12-17	CARIBOO LODGE	BC	1171393	-119.47	52.72	1096	-12.9	-11.8	-1.1	1
6534	1932-12-18	CARIBOO LODGE	BC	1171393	-119.47	52.72	1096	-10.1	-9.8	-0.3	1
6535	1932-12-19	CARIBOO LODGE	BC	1171393	-119.47	52.72	1096	-10.1	-8.3	-1.8	1
6536	1932-12-22	CARIBOO LODGE	BC	1171393	-119.47	52.72	1096	-2.3	-1.4	-0.9	1
6537	1932-12-31	CARIBOO LODGE	BC	1171393	-119.47	52.72	1096	-4.7	-4.2	-0.5	1
6538	1933-01-04	CARIBOO LODGE	BC	1171393	-119.47	52.72	1096	-5.3	-2.3	-3	1
6539	1933-02-09	CARIBOO LODGE	BC	1171393	-119.47	52.72	1096	-20.8	-17	-3.8	1
6540	1933-02-10	CARIBOO LODGE	BC	1171393	-119.47	52.72	1096	-17.5	-15.1	-2.4	1
6541	1933-02-24	CARIBOO LODGE	BC	1171393	-119.47	52.72	1096	-1.8	-1.5	-0.3	1
6542	1933-02-28	CARIBOO LODGE	BC	1171393	-119.47	52.72	1096	-7.1	-7	-0.1	1
6543	1933-03-04	CARIBOO LODGE	BC	1171393	-119.47	52.72	1096	-2.3	-1.5	-0.8	1
6544	1933-03-05	CARIBOO LODGE	BC	1171393	-119.47	52.72	1096	-2.3	-1.1	-1.2	1
6545	1933-03-11	CARIBOO LODGE	BC	1171393	-119.47	52.72	1096	-4.7	-1.5	-3.2	1
6546	1933-10-23	CARIBOO LODGE	BC	1171393	-119.47	52.72	1096	-11.3	-8.3	-3	1
6547	1933-10-24	CARIBOO LODGE	BC	1171393	-119.47	52.72	1096	-0.2	0.8	-1	1
6548	1933-11-01	CARIBOO LODGE	BC	1171393	-119.47	52.72	1096	-0.8	-0.6	-0.2	1
6549	1933-11-20	CARIBOO LODGE	BC	1171393	-119.47	52.72	1096	1.1	1.9	-0.8	1
6550	1933-11-28	CARIBOO LODGE	BC	1171393	-119.47	52.72	1096	-6.5	-3.7	-2.8	1
6551	1933-11-29	CARIBOO LODGE	BC	1171393	-119.47	52.72	1096	-1.8	-0.9	-0.9	1
6552	1933-11-30	CARIBOO LODGE	BC	1171393	-119.47	52.72	1096	-0.2	1.5	-1.7	1
6553	1933-12-10	CARIBOO LODGE	BC	1171393	-119.47	52.72	1096	-15.3	-13.8	-1.5	1
6554	1933-12-11	CARIBOO LODGE	BC	1171393	-119.47	52.72	1096	-16.4	-15	-1.4	1
6555	1933-12-12	CARIBOO LODGE	BC	1171393	-119.47	52.72	1096	-17.5	-14.9	-2.6	1
6556	1933-12-13	CARIBOO LODGE	BC	1171393	-119.47	52.72	1096	-17.5	-17.1	-0.4	1
6557	1933-12-14	CARIBOO LODGE	BC	1171393	-119.47	52.72	1096	-18	-17.8	-0.2	1
6558	1933-12-16	CARIBOO LODGE	BC	1171393	-119.47	52.72	1096	-14.1	-11.8	-2.3	1
6559	1933-12-18	CARIBOO LODGE	BC	1171393	-119.47	52.72	1096	-21.9	-16.4	-5.5	1
6560	1933-12-19	CARIBOO LODGE	BC	1171393	-119.47	52.72	1096	-20.8	-19.4	-1.4	1
6561	1933-12-27	CARIBOO LODGE	BC	1171393	-119.47	52.72	1096	-20.3	-15.7	-4.6	1

6562	1933-12-29	CARIBOO LODGE	BC	1171393	-119.47	52.72	1096	-19.7	-18.6	-1.1	1
6563	1933-12-30	CARIBOO LODGE	BC	1171393	-119.47	52.72	1096	-23.6	-19.4	-4.2	1
6564	1933-12-31	CARIBOO LODGE	BC	1171393	-119.47	52.72	1096	-22.5	-18.6	-3.9	1
6565	1934-01-01	CARIBOO LODGE	BC	1171393	-119.47	52.72	1096	-20.3	-15.8	-4.5	1
6566	1934-01-02	CARIBOO LODGE	BC	1171393	-119.47	52.72	1096	-2.9	-1	-1.9	1
6567	1934-01-04	CARIBOO LODGE	BC	1171393	-119.47	52.72	1096	-0.8	0.1	-0.9	1
6568	1934-01-07	CARIBOO LODGE	BC	1171393	-119.47	52.72	1096	-6.5	-5.3	-1.2	1
6569	1934-01-08	CARIBOO LODGE	BC	1171393	-119.47	52.72	1096	-5.3	-4.2	-1.1	1
6570	1934-01-11	CARIBOO LODGE	BC	1171393	-119.47	52.72	1096	-5.3	-4.8	-0.5	1
6571	1934-01-12	CARIBOO LODGE	BC	1171393	-119.47	52.72	1096	-4.7	-2.3	-2.4	1
6572	1934-01-18	CARIBOO LODGE	BC	1171393	-119.47	52.72	1096	-6.5	-5.8	-0.7	1
6573	1934-01-19	CARIBOO LODGE	BC	1171393	-119.47	52.72	1096	-4.7	-4.2	-0.5	1
6574	1934-01-20	CARIBOO LODGE	BC	1171393	-119.47	52.72	1096	-2.9	-1.4	-1.5	1
6575	1934-01-24	CARIBOO LODGE	BC	1171393	-119.47	52.72	1096	-10.1	-6.9	-3.2	1
6576	1934-01-25	CARIBOO LODGE	BC	1171393	-119.47	52.72	1096	-5.3	-2.3	-3	1
6577	1934-01-31	CARIBOO LODGE	BC	1171393	-119.47	52.72	1096	-0.2	0.1	-0.3	1
6578	1934-02-06	CARIBOO LODGE	BC	1171393	-119.47	52.72	1096	-0.2	0.8	-1	1
6579	1934-02-26	CARIBOO LODGE	BC	1171393	-119.47	52.72	1096	-7.7	-5.8	-1.9	1
6580	1934-02-27	CARIBOO LODGE	BC	1171393	-119.47	52.72	1096	-4.7	-2.3	-2.4	1
6581	1934-03-01	CARIBOO LODGE	BC	1171393	-119.47	52.72	1096	-1.2	0.1	-1.3	1
6582	1934-03-29	CARIBOO LODGE	BC	1171393	-119.47	52.72	1096	0.4	0.8	-0.4	1
6583	1934-10-08	CARIBOO LODGE	BC	1171393	-119.47	52.72	1096	8.7	9.4	-0.7	1
6584	1934-11-21	CARIBOO LODGE	BC	1171393	-119.47	52.72	1096	-5.3	-2.3	-3	1
6585	1934-11-22	CARIBOO LODGE	BC	1171393	-119.47	52.72	1096	-1.2	0	-1.2	1
6586	1934-11-29	CARIBOO LODGE	BC	1171393	-119.47	52.72	1096	-2.3	-1	-1.3	1
6587	1934-12-03	CARIBOO LODGE	BC	1171393	-119.47	52.72	1096	-2.9	-2.3	-0.6	1
6588	1934-12-09	CARIBOO LODGE	BC	1171393	-119.47	52.72	1096	-6.5	-5.8	-0.7	1
6589	1934-12-12	CARIBOO LODGE	BC	1171393	-119.47	52.72	1096	-7.1	-3.7	-3.4	1
6590	1934-12-15	CARIBOO LODGE	BC	1171393	-119.47	52.72	1096	-2.3	-0.9	-1.4	1
6591	1934-12-17	CARIBOO LODGE	BC	1171393	-119.47	52.72	1096	-1.8	-0.9	-0.9	1
6592	1934-12-20	CARIBOO LODGE	BC	1171393	-119.47	52.72	1096	-1.2	-0.9	-0.3	1
6593	1934-12-23	CARIBOO LODGE	BC	1171393	-119.47	52.72	1096	-19.2	-17.4	-1.8	1
6594	1934-12-25	CARIBOO LODGE	BC	1171393	-119.47	52.72	1096	-25.8	-21.2	-4.6	1
6595	1934-12-27	CARIBOO LODGE	BC	1171393	-119.47	52.72	1096	-19.7	-19.4	-0.3	1

6596	1934-12-28	CARIBOO LODGE	BC	1171393	-119.47	52.72	1096	-15.3	-13.7	-1.6	1
6597	1934-12-31	CARIBOO LODGE	BC	1171393	-119.47	52.72	1096	-9.5	-6.4	-3.1	1
6598	1935-01-05	CARIBOO LODGE	BC	1171393	-119.47	52.72	1096	-9	-6.4	-2.6	1
6599	1935-01-14	CARIBOO LODGE	BC	1171393	-119.47	52.72	1096	-23.6	-19	-4.6	1
6600	1935-01-15	CARIBOO LODGE	BC	1171393	-119.47	52.72	1096	-16.4	-15.4	-1	1
6601	1935-01-20	CARIBOO LODGE	BC	1171393	-119.47	52.72	1096	-24.2	-19.5	-4.7	1
6602	1935-01-23	CARIBOO LODGE	BC	1171393	-119.47	52.72	1096	-10.1	-7.7	-2.4	1
6603	1935-01-25	CARIBOO LODGE	BC	1171393	-119.47	52.72	1096	-2.3	-1	-1.3	1
6604	1935-01-26	CARIBOO LODGE	BC	1171393	-119.47	52.72	1096	1.7	2.4	-0.7	1
6605	1935-02-19	CARIBOO LODGE	BC	1171393	-119.47	52.72	1096	-5.3	-2.3	-3	1
6606	1935-07-01	CARIBOO LODGE	BC	1171393	-119.47	52.72	1096	6.1	6.3	-0.2	1
6607	1935-10-23	CARIBOO LODGE	BC	1171393	-119.47	52.72	1096	3.1	4.3	-1.2	1
6608	1935-11-07	CARIBOO LODGE	BC	1171393	-119.47	52.72	1096	2.4	2.8	-0.4	1
6609	1935-11-15	CARIBOO LODGE	BC	1171393	-119.47	52.72	1096	-1.3	-0.9	-0.4	1
6610	1935-11-22	CARIBOO LODGE	BC	1171393	-119.47	52.72	1096	-2.3	-1	-1.3	1
6611	1935-11-23	CARIBOO LODGE	BC	1171393	-119.47	52.72	1096	-1.2	-0.9	-0.3	1
6612	1935-11-24	CARIBOO LODGE	BC	1171393	-119.47	52.72	1096	-0.8	0.8	-1.6	1
6613	1935-12-06	CARIBOO LODGE	BC	1171393	-119.47	52.72	1096	-4.1	-2.3	-1.8	1
6614	1935-12-07	CARIBOO LODGE	BC	1171393	-119.47	52.72	1096	-1.3	-0.9	-0.4	1
6615	1935-12-09	CARIBOO LODGE	BC	1171393	-119.47	52.72	1096	-1.8	0.2	-2	1
6616	1935-12-15	CARIBOO LODGE	BC	1171393	-119.47	52.72	1096	-2.3	-1.4	-0.9	1
6617	1935-12-16	CARIBOO LODGE	BC	1171393	-119.47	52.72	1096	-2.9	-2.3	-0.6	1
6618	1935-12-21	CARIBOO LODGE	BC	1171393	-119.47	52.72	1096	-6.5	-5.3	-1.2	1
6619	1935-12-24	CARIBOO LODGE	BC	1171393	-119.47	52.72	1096	-9	-6.4	-2.6	1
6620	1935-12-25	CARIBOO LODGE	BC	1171393	-119.47	52.72	1096	-3.5	-1.4	-2.1	1
6621	1936-01-06	CARIBOO LODGE	BC	1171393	-119.47	52.72	1096	-8.4	-5.3	-3.1	1
6622	1936-01-07	CARIBOO LODGE	BC	1171393	-119.47	52.72	1096	-5.9	-3.7	-2.2	1
6623	1936-01-15	CARIBOO LODGE	BC	1171393	-119.47	52.72	1096	-14.7	-14.4	-0.3	1
6624	1936-01-22	CARIBOO LODGE	BC	1171393	-119.47	52.72	1096	-1.2	-0.9	-0.3	1
6625	1936-01-29	CARIBOO LODGE	BC	1171393	-119.47	52.72	1096	-14.6	-12.4	-2.2	1
6626	1936-02-07	CARIBOO LODGE	BC	1171393	-119.47	52.72	1096	-26.9	-20.7	-6.2	1
6627	1936-02-08	CARIBOO LODGE	BC	1171393	-119.47	52.72	1096	-18	-16.8	-1.2	1
6628	1936-02-09	CARIBOO LODGE	BC	1171393	-119.47	52.72	1096	-18	-14.7	-3.3	1
6629	1936-02-28	CARIBOO LODGE	BC	1171393	-119.47	52.72	1096	-0.1	2.3	-2.4	1

6630	1936-06-27	CARIBOO LODGE	BC	1171393	-119.47	52.72	1096	8.1	8.9	-0.8	1
6631	1936-09-15	CARIBOO LODGE	BC	1171393	-119.47	52.72	1096	1.1	3.3	-2.2	1
6632	1936-10-21	CARIBOO LODGE	BC	1171393	-119.47	52.72	1096	-2.3	-0.9	-1.4	1
6633	1936-11-02	CARIBOO LODGE	BC	1171393	-119.47	52.72	1096	-5.3	-2.1	-3.2	1
6634	1936-11-03	CARIBOO LODGE	BC	1171393	-119.47	52.72	1096	-2.3	-2.1	-0.2	1
6635	1936-11-07	CARIBOO LODGE	BC	1171393	-119.47	52.72	1096	-5.9	-3.6	-2.3	1
6636	1936-11-10	CARIBOO LODGE	BC	1171393	-119.47	52.72	1096	-1.8	-0.9	-0.9	1
6637	1936-11-11	CARIBOO LODGE	BC	1171393	-119.47	52.72	1096	1.1	2.4	-1.3	1
6638	1936-11-17	CARIBOO LODGE	BC	1171393	-119.47	52.72	1096	4.2	4.9	-0.7	1
6639	1936-11-25	CARIBOO LODGE	BC	1171393	-119.47	52.72	1096	-6.5	-4.8	-1.7	1
6640	1936-11-29	CARIBOO LODGE	BC	1171393	-119.47	52.72	1096	-5.9	-3.7	-2.2	1
6641	1936-11-30	CARIBOO LODGE	BC	1171393	-119.47	52.72	1096	-2.3	-2.1	-0.2	1
6642	1936-12-01	CARIBOO LODGE	BC	1171393	-119.47	52.72	1096	-4	-3.7	-0.3	1
6643	1936-12-05	CARIBOO LODGE	BC	1171393	-119.47	52.72	1096	-20.8	-18.2	-2.6	1
6644	1936-12-12	CARIBOO LODGE	BC	1171393	-119.47	52.72	1096	-4.7	-2.1	-2.6	1
6645	1936-12-17	CARIBOO LODGE	BC	1171393	-119.47	52.72	1096	-2.9	-2.1	-0.8	1
6646	1936-12-20	CARIBOO LODGE	BC	1171393	-119.47	52.72	1096	-9	-5.8	-3.2	1
6647	1936-12-29	CARIBOO LODGE	BC	1171393	-119.47	52.72	1096	-16.4	-15.7	-0.7	1
6648	1937-01-02	CARIBOO LODGE	BC	1171393	-119.47	52.72	1096	-15.8	-15.7	-0.1	1
6649	1937-01-03	CARIBOO LODGE	BC	1171393	-119.47	52.72	1096	-11.3	-9.8	-1.5	1
6650	1937-01-06	CARIBOO LODGE	BC	1171393	-119.47	52.72	1096	-23	-20.3	-2.7	1
6651	1937-01-08	CARIBOO LODGE	BC	1171393	-119.47	52.72	1096	-18	-15.4	-2.6	1
6652	1937-01-16	CARIBOO LODGE	BC	1171393	-119.47	52.72	1096	-23	-19.8	-3.2	1
6653	1937-01-21	CARIBOO LODGE	BC	1171393	-119.47	52.72	1096	-17.5	-15.4	-2.1	1
6654	1937-01-22	CARIBOO LODGE	BC	1171393	-119.47	52.72	1096	-15.3	-13.4	-1.9	1
6655	1937-01-24	CARIBOO LODGE	BC	1171393	-119.47	52.72	1096	-16.4	-15	-1.4	1
6656	1937-01-31	CARIBOO LODGE	BC	1171393	-119.47	52.72	1096	-19.2	-17.9	-1.3	1
6657	1937-02-01	CARIBOO LODGE	BC	1171393	-119.47	52.72	1096	-20.8	-18.1	-2.7	1
6658	1937-02-04	CARIBOO LODGE	BC	1171393	-119.47	52.72	1096	-20.3	-16.5	-3.8	1
6659	1937-02-08	CARIBOO LODGE	BC	1171393	-119.47	52.72	1096	-19.2	-16.9	-2.3	1
6660	1937-02-09	CARIBOO LODGE	BC	1171393	-119.47	52.72	1096	-12.4	-11.2	-1.2	1
6661	1937-02-14	CARIBOO LODGE	BC	1171393	-119.47	52.72	1096	-4	-2.1	-1.9	1
6662	1937-11-07	CARIBOO LODGE	BC	1171393	-119.47	52.72	1096	-0.8	0	-0.8	1
6663	1937-11-19	CARIBOO LODGE	BC	1171393	-119.47	52.72	1096	-11.3	-8.3	-3	1

6664	1937-11-20	CARIBOO LODGE	BC	1171393	-119.47	52.72	1096	-4	-1.4	-2.6	1
6665	1937-11-22	CARIBOO LODGE	BC	1171393	-119.47	52.72	1096	-0.8	0	-0.8	1
6666	1937-12-01	CARIBOO LODGE	BC	1171393	-119.47	52.72	1096	-5.2	-3.7	-1.5	1
6667	1937-12-04	CARIBOO LODGE	BC	1171393	-119.47	52.72	1096	-4.7	-1.4	-3.3	1
6668	1937-12-09	CARIBOO LODGE	BC	1171393	-119.47	52.72	1096	-16.4	-15.1	-1.3	1
6669	1937-12-13	CARIBOO LODGE	BC	1171393	-119.47	52.72	1096	-1.2	-0.8	-0.4	1
6670	1937-12-15	CARIBOO LODGE	BC	1171393	-119.47	52.72	1096	-1.3	-0.6	-0.7	1
6671	1937-12-18	CARIBOO LODGE	BC	1171393	-119.47	52.72	1096	-2.3	-0.8	-1.5	1
6672	1937-12-27	CARIBOO LODGE	BC	1171393	-119.47	52.72	1096	-24.2	-18.1	-6.1	1
6673	1937-12-31	CARIBOO LODGE	BC	1171393	-119.47	52.72	1096	-1.8	-0.6	-1.2	1
6674	1938-01-08	CARIBOO LODGE	BC	1171393	-119.47	52.72	1096	-7.2	-6.4	-0.8	1
6675	1938-01-09	CARIBOO LODGE	BC	1171393	-119.47	52.72	1096	-5.2	-3.7	-1.5	1
6676	1938-01-11	CARIBOO LODGE	BC	1171393	-119.47	52.72	1096	-11.8	-8.3	-3.5	1
6677	1938-01-12	CARIBOO LODGE	BC	1171393	-119.47	52.72	1096	-7.1	-5.8	-1.3	1
6678	1938-01-13	CARIBOO LODGE	BC	1171393	-119.47	52.72	1096	-2.3	-2.2	-0.1	1
6679	1938-01-20	CARIBOO LODGE	BC	1171393	-119.47	52.72	1096	-5.3	-2.9	-2.4	1
6680	1938-01-21	CARIBOO LODGE	BC	1171393	-119.47	52.72	1096	-3.5	-1.4	-2.1	1
6681	1938-01-24	CARIBOO LODGE	BC	1171393	-119.47	52.72	1096	-7.1	-4.8	-2.3	1
6682	1938-01-31	CARIBOO LODGE	BC	1171393	-119.47	52.72	1096	-17.5	-15.8	-1.7	1
6683	1938-02-01	CARIBOO LODGE	BC	1171393	-119.47	52.72	1096	-15.3	-14.8	-0.5	1
6684	1938-02-17	CARIBOO LODGE	BC	1171393	-119.47	52.72	1096	-6.5	-5.8	-0.7	1
6685	1938-03-18	CARIBOO LODGE	BC	1171393	-119.47	52.72	1096	-2.3	-1.4	-0.9	1
6686	1938-11-06	CARIBOO LODGE	BC	1171393	-119.47	52.72	1096	-1.8	-0.6	-1.2	1
6687	1938-11-11	CARIBOO LODGE	BC	1171393	-119.47	52.72	1096	-9.5	-6.9	-2.6	1
6688	1938-11-13	CARIBOO LODGE	BC	1171393	-119.47	52.72	1096	-4.1	-1	-3.1	1
6689	1938-11-15	CARIBOO LODGE	BC	1171393	-119.47	52.72	1096	-0.8	-0.6	-0.2	1
6690	1938-11-17	CARIBOO LODGE	BC	1171393	-119.47	52.72	1096	-0.2	0	-0.2	1
6691	1938-11-23	CARIBOO LODGE	BC	1171393	-119.47	52.72	1096	-9	-7	-2	1
6692	1938-11-24	CARIBOO LODGE	BC	1171393	-119.47	52.72	1096	-7.1	-7	-0.1	1
6693	1938-11-27	CARIBOO LODGE	BC	1171393	-119.47	52.72	1096	-3.5	-2.9	-0.6	1
6694	1938-11-29	CARIBOO LODGE	BC	1171393	-119.47	52.72	1096	-2.3	-0.6	-1.7	1
6695	1938-11-30	CARIBOO LODGE	BC	1171393	-119.47	52.72	1096	-1.3	0	-1.3	1
6696	1938-12-04	CARIBOO LODGE	BC	1171393	-119.47	52.72	1096	-2.3	-0.8	-1.5	1
6697	1938-12-05	CARIBOO LODGE	BC	1171393	-119.47	52.72	1096	-0.8	-0.7	-0.1	1

6698	1938-12-07	CARIBOO LODGE	BC	1171393	-119.47	52.72	1096	-1.8	0.1	-1.9	1
6699	1938-12-12	CARIBOO LODGE	BC	1171393	-119.47	52.72	1096	-9	-7.7	-1.3	1
6700	1938-12-13	CARIBOO LODGE	BC	1171393	-119.47	52.72	1096	-7.7	-6.9	-0.8	1
6701	1938-12-17	CARIBOO LODGE	BC	1171393	-119.47	52.72	1096	-9.5	-7.7	-1.8	1
6702	1938-12-20	CARIBOO LODGE	BC	1171393	-119.47	52.72	1096	-9.5	-6.9	-2.6	1
6703	1938-12-22	CARIBOO LODGE	BC	1171393	-119.47	52.72	1096	-7.2	-6.9	-0.3	1
6704	1938-12-29	CARIBOO LODGE	BC	1171393	-119.47	52.72	1096	-18.6	-15.2	-3.4	1
6705	1938-12-31	CARIBOO LODGE	BC	1171393	-119.47	52.72	1096	-7.7	-5.3	-2.4	1
6706	1939-01-01	CARIBOO LODGE	BC	1171393	-119.47	52.72	1096	-0.8	0.8	-1.6	1
6707	1939-01-02	CARIBOO LODGE	BC	1171393	-119.47	52.72	1096	1.1	1.5	-0.4	1
6708	1939-01-06	CARIBOO LODGE	BC	1171393	-119.47	52.72	1096	-7.2	-4.2	-3	1
6709	1939-01-10	CARIBOO LODGE	BC	1171393	-119.47	52.72	1096	-2.3	-2.2	-0.1	1
6710	1939-01-12	CARIBOO LODGE	BC	1171393	-119.47	52.72	1096	-2.3	-0.6	-1.7	1
6711	1939-01-16	CARIBOO LODGE	BC	1171393	-119.47	52.72	1096	-4.7	-4.2	-0.5	1
6712	1939-01-18	CARIBOO LODGE	BC	1171393	-119.47	52.72	1096	-3.5	-0.9	-2.6	1
6713	1939-01-26	CARIBOO LODGE	BC	1171393	-119.47	52.72	1096	-5.9	-5.8	-0.1	1
6714	1939-02-02	CARIBOO LODGE	BC	1171393	-119.47	52.72	1096	-8.3	-7.6	-0.7	1
6715	1939-02-10	CARIBOO LODGE	BC	1171393	-119.47	52.72	1096	-18.6	-15.3	-3.3	1
6716	1939-02-11	CARIBOO LODGE	BC	1171393	-119.47	52.72	1096	-12.4	-11.3	-1.1	1
6717	1939-02-23	CARIBOO LODGE	BC	1171393	-119.47	52.72	1096	-1.8	-0.9	-0.9	1
6718	1939-03-05	CARIBOO LODGE	BC	1171393	-119.47	52.72	1096	-6.5	-5.8	-0.7	1
6719	1939-04-25	CARIBOO LODGE	BC	1171393	-119.47	52.72	1096	7.1	7.9	-0.8	1
6720	1939-11-07	CARIBOO LODGE	BC	1171393	-119.47	52.72	1096	-1.8	-1	-0.8	1
6721	1939-11-09	CARIBOO LODGE	BC	1171393	-119.47	52.72	1096	-1.8	-0.9	-0.9	1
6722	1939-11-12	CARIBOO LODGE	BC	1171393	-119.47	52.72	1096	4.7	4.9	-0.2	1
6723	1939-11-15	CARIBOO LODGE	BC	1171393	-119.47	52.72	1096	4.2	4.3	-0.1	1
6724	1939-11-21	CARIBOO LODGE	BC	1171393	-119.47	52.72	1096	1.1	1.5	-0.4	1
6725	1939-11-28	CARIBOO LODGE	BC	1171393	-119.47	52.72	1096	1.1	1.5	-0.4	1
6726	1939-11-29	CARIBOO LODGE	BC	1171393	-119.47	52.72	1096	0.4	0.7	-0.3	1
6727	1939-12-04	CARIBOO LODGE	BC	1171393	-119.47	52.72	1096	3.6	5.4	-1.8	1
6728	1939-12-12	CARIBOO LODGE	BC	1171393	-119.47	52.72	1096	-1.2	-0.6	-0.6	1
6729	1939-12-13	CARIBOO LODGE	BC	1171393	-119.47	52.72	1096	-1.2	0.1	-1.3	1
6730	1939-12-15	CARIBOO LODGE	BC	1171393	-119.47	52.72	1096	-1.8	-0.9	-0.9	1
6731	1939-12-16	CARIBOO LODGE	BC	1171393	-119.47	52.72	1096	-1.8	-0.9	-0.9	1

6732	1939-12-18	CARIBOO LODGE	BC	1171393	-119.47	52.72	1096	-2.3	-1.1	-1.2	1
6733	1939-12-19	CARIBOO LODGE	BC	1171393	-119.47	52.72	1096	-1.3	-0.6	-0.7	1
6734	1939-12-27	CARIBOO LODGE	BC	1171393	-119.47	52.72	1096	-10.7	-10.6	-0.1	1
6735	1939-12-29	CARIBOO LODGE	BC	1171393	-119.47	52.72	1096	-7.2	-5.8	-1.4	1
6736	1939-12-31	CARIBOO LODGE	BC	1171393	-119.47	52.72	1096	-9	-5.8	-3.2	1
6737	1940-01-01	CARIBOO LODGE	BC	1171393	-119.47	52.72	1096	-2.3	-1.1	-1.2	1
6738	1940-01-02	CARIBOO LODGE	BC	1171393	-119.47	52.72	1096	-0.8	-0.6	-0.2	1
6739	1940-01-12	CARIBOO LODGE	BC	1171393	-119.47	52.72	1096	-9.5	-6.9	-2.6	1
6740	1940-01-13	CARIBOO LODGE	BC	1171393	-119.47	52.72	1096	-7.7	-5.8	-1.9	1
6741	1940-01-25	CARIBOO LODGE	BC	1171393	-119.47	52.72	1096	-11.8	-11.3	-0.5	1
6742	1940-01-26	CARIBOO LODGE	BC	1171393	-119.47	52.72	1096	-9.5	-5.8	-3.7	1
6743	1940-01-27	CARIBOO LODGE	BC	1171393	-119.47	52.72	1096	-6	-2.2	-3.8	1
6744	1940-02-05	CARIBOO LODGE	BC	1171393	-119.47	52.72	1096	-1.2	-0.6	-0.6	1
6745	1940-02-26	CARIBOO LODGE	BC	1171393	-119.47	52.72	1096	-14.1	-12.9	-1.2	1
6746	1940-04-30	CARIBOO LODGE	BC	1171393	-119.47	52.72	1096	1.8	2.8	-1	1
6747	1940-11-14	CARIBOO LODGE	BC	1171393	-119.47	52.72	1096	-6	-3.7	-2.3	1
6748	1940-11-16	CARIBOO LODGE	BC	1171393	-119.47	52.72	1096	-1.8	-1.4	-0.4	1
6749	1940-11-19	CARIBOO LODGE	BC	1171393	-119.47	52.72	1096	-5.3	-4.8	-0.5	1
6750	1940-11-23	CARIBOO LODGE	BC	1171393	-119.47	52.72	1096	-4.7	-2.2	-2.5	1
6751	1940-11-24	CARIBOO LODGE	BC	1171393	-119.47	52.72	1096	-2.9	-0.8	-2.1	1
6752	1940-11-25	CARIBOO LODGE	BC	1171393	-119.47	52.72	1096	-1.8	0.1	-1.9	1
6753	1940-11-26	CARIBOO LODGE	BC	1171393	-119.47	52.72	1096	-1.2	-0.6	-0.6	1
6754	1940-12-06	CARIBOO LODGE	BC	1171393	-119.47	52.72	1096	-0.2	0.1	-0.3	1
6755	1940-12-07	CARIBOO LODGE	BC	1171393	-119.47	52.72	1096	-0.8	0.1	-0.9	1
6756	1940-12-17	CARIBOO LODGE	BC	1171393	-119.47	52.72	1096	-10.7	-7.6	-3.1	1
6757	1940-12-18	CARIBOO LODGE	BC	1171393	-119.47	52.72	1096	-5.9	-3	-2.9	1
6758	1940-12-19	CARIBOO LODGE	BC	1171393	-119.47	52.72	1096	-1.3	-0.6	-0.7	1
6759	1940-12-20	CARIBOO LODGE	BC	1171393	-119.47	52.72	1096	-0.2	0.7	-0.9	1
6760	1940-12-21	CARIBOO LODGE	BC	1171393	-119.47	52.72	1096	1.2	2.3	-1.1	1
6761	1940-12-23	CARIBOO LODGE	BC	1171393	-119.47	52.72	1096	-2.3	-0.9	-1.4	1
6762	1940-12-25	CARIBOO LODGE	BC	1171393	-119.47	52.72	1096	0.4	0.7	-0.3	1
6763	1941-01-01	CARIBOO LODGE	BC	1171393	-119.47	52.72	1096	-7.7	-7.6	-0.1	1
6764	1941-01-08	CARIBOO LODGE	BC	1171393	-119.47	52.72	1096	-2.9	-0.9	-2	1
6765	1941-01-09	CARIBOO LODGE	BC	1171393	-119.47	52.72	1096	-1.3	1.5	-2.8	1

6766	1941-01-11	CARIBOO LODGE	BC	1171393	-119.47	52.72	1096	1.2	1.5	-0.3	1
6767	1941-01-17	CARIBOO LODGE	BC	1171393	-119.47	52.72	1096	-1.8	-0.9	-0.9	1
6768	1941-01-18	CARIBOO LODGE	BC	1171393	-119.47	52.72	1096	-1.3	-0.9	-0.4	1
6769	1941-01-26	CARIBOO LODGE	BC	1171393	-119.47	52.72	1096	-12.4	-10.5	-1.9	1
6770	1941-01-27	CARIBOO LODGE	BC	1171393	-119.47	52.72	1096	-1.8	0.2	-2	1
6771	1941-01-29	CARIBOO LODGE	BC	1171393	-119.47	52.72	1096	0.4	1.5	-1.1	1
6772	1941-01-31	CARIBOO LODGE	BC	1171393	-119.47	52.72	1096	-0.2	1.5	-1.7	1
6773	1941-02-02	CARIBOO LODGE	BC	1171393	-119.47	52.72	1096	-0.2	0.2	-0.4	1
6774	1941-02-25	CARIBOO LODGE	BC	1171393	-119.47	52.72	1096	-3.5	-1.4	-2.1	1
6775	1941-02-26	CARIBOO LODGE	BC	1171393	-119.47	52.72	1096	-0.8	-0.6	-0.2	1
6776	1941-04-15	CARIBOO LODGE	BC	1171393	-119.47	52.72	1096	-0.8	-0.6	-0.2	1
6777	1941-11-13	CARIBOO LODGE	BC	1171393	-119.47	52.72	1096	-1.8	0.7	-2.5	1
6778	1941-11-23	CARIBOO LODGE	BC	1171393	-119.47	52.72	1096	-7.7	-5.3	-2.4	1
6779	1941-11-24	CARIBOO LODGE	BC	1171393	-119.47	52.72	1096	-4.7	-4.2	-0.5	1
6780	1941-11-25	CARIBOO LODGE	BC	1171393	-119.47	52.72	1096	-0.2	1.5	-1.7	1
6781	1941-11-27	CARIBOO LODGE	BC	1171393	-119.47	52.72	1096	-2.3	-1.1	-1.2	1
6782	1941-11-28	CARIBOO LODGE	BC	1171393	-119.47	52.72	1096	1.2	1.5	-0.3	1
6783	1941-12-01	CARIBOO LODGE	BC	1171393	-119.47	52.72	1096	1.7	2.4	-0.7	1
6784	1941-12-05	CARIBOO LODGE	BC	1171393	-119.47	52.72	1096	-3.5	-1	-2.5	1
6785	1941-12-07	CARIBOO LODGE	BC	1171393	-119.47	52.72	1096	-1.2	-0.6	-0.6	1
6786	1941-12-13	CARIBOO LODGE	BC	1171393	-119.47	52.72	1096	-9	-6.4	-2.6	1
6787	1941-12-14	CARIBOO LODGE	BC	1171393	-119.47	52.72	1096	-5.3	-4.8	-0.5	1
6788	1941-12-15	CARIBOO LODGE	BC	1171393	-119.47	52.72	1096	-3.5	-1.1	-2.4	1
6789	1941-12-18	CARIBOO LODGE	BC	1171393	-119.47	52.72	1096	-2.3	-1	-1.3	1
6790	1941-12-21	CARIBOO LODGE	BC	1171393	-119.47	52.72	1096	-3.5	-1.4	-2.1	1
6791	1942-01-01	CARIBOO LODGE	BC	1171393	-119.47	52.72	1096	-17.5	-15.5	-2	1
6792	1942-01-09	CARIBOO LODGE	BC	1171393	-119.47	52.72	1096	-12.9	-11.8	-1.1	1
6793	1942-01-11	CARIBOO LODGE	BC	1171393	-119.47	52.72	1096	-2.9	-1.4	-1.5	1
6794	1942-01-13	CARIBOO LODGE	BC	1171393	-119.47	52.72	1096	-4.1	-2.2	-1.9	1
6795	1942-01-14	CARIBOO LODGE	BC	1171393	-119.47	52.72	1096	-2.9	-2.2	-0.7	1
6796	1942-01-17	CARIBOO LODGE	BC	1171393	-119.47	52.72	1096	-3.5	-1.4	-2.1	1
6797	1942-01-18	CARIBOO LODGE	BC	1171393	-119.47	52.72	1096	-2.3	-0.9	-1.4	1
6798	1942-01-23	CARIBOO LODGE	BC	1171393	-119.47	52.72	1096	-3.5	-2.2	-1.3	1
6799	1942-01-24	CARIBOO LODGE	BC	1171393	-119.47	52.72	1096	-1.2	-0.9	-0.3	1

6800	1942-01-26	CARIBOO LODGE	BC	1171393	-119.47	52.72	1096	0.4	1.5	-1.1	1
6801	1942-01-31	CARIBOO LODGE	BC	1171393	-119.47	52.72	1096	-1.2	-1	-0.2	1
6802	1942-02-03	CARIBOO LODGE	BC	1171393	-119.47	52.72	1096	-1.2	-1	-0.2	1
6803	1942-11-02	CARIBOO LODGE	BC	1171393	-119.47	52.72	1096	-5.3	-2.9	-2.4	1
6804	1942-11-09	CARIBOO LODGE	BC	1171393	-119.47	52.72	1096	-4.7	-2.1	-2.6	1
6805	1942-11-10	CARIBOO LODGE	BC	1171393	-119.47	52.72	1096	-0.1	0	-0.1	1
6806	1942-11-20	CARIBOO LODGE	BC	1171393	-119.47	52.72	1096	-5.9	-3.7	-2.2	1
6807	1942-11-21	CARIBOO LODGE	BC	1171393	-119.47	52.72	1096	-4	-0.6	-3.4	1
6808	1942-12-07	CARIBOO LODGE	BC	1171393	-119.47	52.72	1096	-12.4	-10.5	-1.9	1
6809	1942-12-11	CARIBOO LODGE	BC	1171393	-119.47	52.72	1096	-2.9	-0.6	-2.3	1
6810	1942-12-12	CARIBOO LODGE	BC	1171393	-119.47	52.72	1096	-0.8	-0.6	-0.2	1
6811	1942-12-13	CARIBOO LODGE	BC	1171393	-119.47	52.72	1096	0.4	1.5	-1.1	1
6812	1942-12-15	CARIBOO LODGE	BC	1171393	-119.47	52.72	1096	0.4	0.9	-0.5	1
6813	1942-12-21	CARIBOO LODGE	BC	1171393	-119.47	52.72	1096	-2.3	-0.9	-1.4	1
6814	1942-12-27	CARIBOO LODGE	BC	1171393	-119.47	52.72	1096	-8.4	-6.4	-2	1
6815	1943-01-04	CARIBOO LODGE	BC	1171393	-119.47	52.72	1096	-12.9	-12.4	-0.5	1
6816	1943-01-05	CARIBOO LODGE	BC	1171393	-119.47	52.72	1096	-7.1	-5.8	-1.3	1
6817	1943-01-06	CARIBOO LODGE	BC	1171393	-119.47	52.72	1096	-5.3	-4.8	-0.5	1
6818	1943-01-07	CARIBOO LODGE	BC	1171393	-119.47	52.72	1096	-3.5	-1.1	-2.4	1
6819	1943-01-11	CARIBOO LODGE	BC	1171393	-119.47	52.72	1096	-7.1	-5.8	-1.3	1
6820	1943-01-12	CARIBOO LODGE	BC	1171393	-119.47	52.72	1096	-6	-3.7	-2.3	1
6821	1943-01-18	CARIBOO LODGE	BC	1171393	-119.47	52.72	1096	-24.7	-20.3	-4.4	1
6822	1943-01-25	CARIBOO LODGE	BC	1171393	-119.47	52.72	1096	-19.2	-16.4	-2.8	1
6823	1943-01-31	CARIBOO LODGE	BC	1171393	-119.47	52.72	1096	-8.3	-7.6	-0.7	1
6824	1943-02-01	CARIBOO LODGE	BC	1171393	-119.47	52.72	1096	-6.5	-4.8	-1.7	1
6825	1943-02-10	CARIBOO LODGE	BC	1171393	-119.47	52.72	1096	-7.1	-5.3	-1.8	1
6826	1943-03-09	CARIBOO LODGE	BC	1171393	-119.47	52.72	1096	-3.5	-3	-0.5	1
6827	1943-03-22	CARIBOO LODGE	BC	1171393	-119.47	52.72	1096	1.2	1.5	-0.3	1
6828	1943-04-01	CARIBOO LODGE	BC	1171393	-119.47	52.72	1096	1.8	1.9	-0.1	1
6829	1943-10-24	CARIBOO LODGE	BC	1171393	-119.47	52.72	1096	-2.3	0.2	-2.5	1
6830	1943-11-01	CARIBOO LODGE	BC	1171393	-119.47	52.72	1096	-1.2	-0.7	-0.5	1
6831	1943-11-02	CARIBOO LODGE	BC	1171393	-119.47	52.72	1096	-0.2	0.2	-0.4	1
6832	1943-11-13	CARIBOO LODGE	BC	1171393	-119.47	52.72	1096	-0.8	-0.7	-0.1	1
6833	1943-11-16	CARIBOO LODGE	BC	1171393	-119.47	52.72	1096	0.5	0.9	-0.4	1

6834	1943-11-19	CARIBOO LODGE	BC	1171393	-119.47	52.72	1096	1.2	1.5	-0.3	1
6835	1943-11-20	CARIBOO LODGE	BC	1171393	-119.47	52.72	1096	1.2	1.5	-0.3	1
6836	1943-11-28	CARIBOO LODGE	BC	1171393	-119.47	52.72	1096	-2.9	-1.4	-1.5	1
6837	1943-11-29	CARIBOO LODGE	BC	1171393	-119.47	52.72	1096	-2.9	-1.4	-1.5	1
6838	1943-12-01	CARIBOO LODGE	BC	1171393	-119.47	52.72	1096	-3.5	-1	-2.5	1
6839	1943-12-02	CARIBOO LODGE	BC	1171393	-119.47	52.72	1096	-0.1	0.2	-0.3	1
6840	1943-12-06	CARIBOO LODGE	BC	1171393	-119.47	52.72	1096	-4.7	-2.1	-2.6	1
6841	1943-12-15	CARIBOO LODGE	BC	1171393	-119.47	52.72	1096	-7.1	-5.8	-1.3	1
6842	1943-12-16	CARIBOO LODGE	BC	1171393	-119.47	52.72	1096	-4.7	-4.2	-0.5	1
6843	1943-12-23	CARIBOO LODGE	BC	1171393	-119.47	52.72	1096	-5.3	-3.7	-1.6	1
6844	1943-12-24	CARIBOO LODGE	BC	1171393	-119.47	52.72	1096	-2.3	-1.4	-0.9	1
6845	1943-12-25	CARIBOO LODGE	BC	1171393	-119.47	52.72	1096	-1.8	-1.4	-0.4	1
6846	1943-12-26	CARIBOO LODGE	BC	1171393	-119.47	52.72	1096	-2.3	-1.4	-0.9	1
6847	1943-12-27	CARIBOO LODGE	BC	1171393	-119.47	52.72	1096	-2.9	-1.4	-1.5	1
6848	1943-12-30	CARIBOO LODGE	BC	1171393	-119.47	52.72	1096	-9	-6.4	-2.6	1
6849	1943-12-31	CARIBOO LODGE	BC	1171393	-119.47	52.72	1096	-7.1	-5.3	-1.8	1
6850	1944-01-06	CARIBOO LODGE	BC	1171393	-119.47	52.72	1096	-8.3	-6.4	-1.9	1
6851	1944-01-07	CARIBOO LODGE	BC	1171393	-119.47	52.72	1096	-7.1	-4.8	-2.3	1
6852	1944-01-11	CARIBOO LODGE	BC	1171393	-119.47	52.72	1096	-7.7	-5.8	-1.9	1
6853	1944-01-12	CARIBOO LODGE	BC	1171393	-119.47	52.72	1096	-6.5	-4.2	-2.3	1
6854	1944-01-13	CARIBOO LODGE	BC	1171393	-119.47	52.72	1096	-2.9	-0.9	-2	1
6855	1944-01-15	CARIBOO LODGE	BC	1171393	-119.47	52.72	1096	-0.1	0.2	-0.3	1
6856	1944-01-16	CARIBOO LODGE	BC	1171393	-119.47	52.72	1096	-0.8	1.5	-2.3	1
6857	1944-01-21	CARIBOO LODGE	BC	1171393	-119.47	52.72	1096	-1.8	-1.4	-0.4	1
6858	1944-01-22	CARIBOO LODGE	BC	1171393	-119.47	52.72	1096	-1.8	-0.9	-0.9	1
6859	1944-02-01	CARIBOO LODGE	BC	1171393	-119.47	52.72	1096	-4	-3.7	-0.3	1
6860	1944-02-15	CARIBOO LODGE	BC	1171393	-119.47	52.72	1096	-6.5	-6.4	-0.1	1
6861	1944-11-05	CARIBOO LODGE	BC	1171393	-119.47	52.72	1096	4.7	4.9	-0.2	1
6862	1944-11-10	CARIBOO LODGE	BC	1171393	-119.47	52.72	1096	-2.9	-2.2	-0.7	1
6863	1944-11-25	CARIBOO LODGE	BC	1171393	-119.47	52.72	1096	-4.1	-1	-3.1	1
6864	1944-12-03	CARIBOO LODGE	BC	1171393	-119.47	52.72	1096	-2.3	-0.6	-1.7	1
6865	1944-12-04	CARIBOO LODGE	BC	1171393	-119.47	52.72	1096	-0.8	0.8	-1.6	1
6866	1944-12-07	CARIBOO LODGE	BC	1171393	-119.47	52.72	1096	-5.9	-5.3	-0.6	1
6867	1945-01-02	CARIBOO LODGE	BC	1171393	-119.47	52.72	1096	-12.4	-9.7	-2.7	1

6868	1945-01-04	CARIBOO LODGE	BC	1171393	-119.47	52.72	1096	-4.1	-1.4	-2.7	1
6869	1945-01-05	CARIBOO LODGE	BC	1171393	-119.47	52.72	1096	-2.3	-1.1	-1.2	1
6870	1945-01-08	CARIBOO LODGE	BC	1171393	-119.47	52.72	1096	-4.7	-1.4	-3.3	1
6871	1945-01-31	CARIBOO LODGE	BC	1171393	-119.47	52.72	1096	-9.5	-9	-0.5	1
6872	1945-02-03	CARIBOO LODGE	BC	1171393	-119.47	52.72	1096	-3.5	-3	-0.5	1
6873	1945-02-06	CARIBOO LODGE	BC	1171393	-119.47	52.72	1096	-0.8	-0.6	-0.2	1
6874	1945-02-07	CARIBOO LODGE	BC	1171393	-119.47	52.72	1096	-0.8	0.2	-1	1
6875	1945-03-06	CARIBOO LODGE	BC	1171393	-119.47	52.72	1096	-6.5	-4.2	-2.3	1
6876	1945-03-07	CARIBOO LODGE	BC	1171393	-119.47	52.72	1096	-3.5	-3	-0.5	1
6877	1945-03-11	CARIBOO LODGE	BC	1171393	-119.47	52.72	1096	-0.8	0.2	-1	1
6878	1945-03-19	CARIBOO LODGE	BC	1171393	-119.47	52.72	1096	-0.8	0.8	-1.6	1
6879	1945-10-18	CARIBOO LODGE	BC	1171393	-119.47	52.72	1096	-0.1	0.8	-0.9	1
6880	1945-10-28	CARIBOO LODGE	BC	1171393	-119.47	52.72	1096	-3.5	-1.4	-2.1	1
6881	1945-11-02	CARIBOO LODGE	BC	1171393	-119.47	52.72	1096	-1.8	-0.8	-1	1
6882	1945-11-08	CARIBOO LODGE	BC	1171393	-119.47	52.72	1096	-14.7	-12.4	-2.3	1
6883	1945-11-09	CARIBOO LODGE	BC	1171393	-119.47	52.72	1096	-9.5	-6.9	-2.6	1
6884	1945-11-10	CARIBOO LODGE	BC	1171393	-119.47	52.72	1096	-6.5	-5.8	-0.7	1
6885	1945-11-18	CARIBOO LODGE	BC	1171393	-119.47	52.72	1096	-7.1	-6.9	-0.2	1
6886	1945-11-21	CARIBOO LODGE	BC	1171393	-119.47	52.72	1096	-7.1	-4.8	-2.3	1
6887	1945-11-22	CARIBOO LODGE	BC	1171393	-119.47	52.72	1096	-3.5	-0.9	-2.6	1
6888	1945-11-23	CARIBOO LODGE	BC	1171393	-119.47	52.72	1096	-2.9	-0.9	-2	1
6889	1945-11-24	CARIBOO LODGE	BC	1171393	-119.47	52.72	1096	-2.3	-0.6	-1.7	1
6890	1945-11-27	CARIBOO LODGE	BC	1171393	-119.47	52.72	1096	-1.8	-1.5	-0.3	1
6891	1945-11-28	CARIBOO LODGE	BC	1171393	-119.47	52.72	1096	-2.3	-0.9	-1.4	1
6892	1945-11-30	CARIBOO LODGE	BC	1171393	-119.47	52.72	1096	-1.3	-0.9	-0.4	1
6893	1945-12-02	CARIBOO LODGE	BC	1171393	-119.47	52.72	1096	-1.3	-0.6	-0.7	1
6894	1945-12-03	CARIBOO LODGE	BC	1171393	-119.47	52.72	1096	-1.3	-0.6	-0.7	1
6895	1945-12-04	CARIBOO LODGE	BC	1171393	-119.47	52.72	1096	-1.8	-0.9	-0.9	1
6896	1945-12-05	CARIBOO LODGE	BC	1171393	-119.47	52.72	1096	-0.8	-0.6	-0.2	1
6897	1945-12-11	CARIBOO LODGE	BC	1171393	-119.47	52.72	1096	-10.7	-9.7	-1	1
6898	1945-12-13	CARIBOO LODGE	BC	1171393	-119.47	52.72	1096	-11.8	-11.3	-0.5	1
6899	1945-12-14	CARIBOO LODGE	BC	1171393	-119.47	52.72	1096	-9.5	-8.3	-1.2	1
6900	1945-12-24	CARIBOO LODGE	BC	1171393	-119.47	52.72	1096	-1.8	-0.7	-1.1	1
6901	1945-12-27	CARIBOO LODGE	BC	1171393	-119.47	52.72	1096	-0.8	-0.6	-0.2	1

6902	1945-12-30	CARIBOO LODGE	BC	1171393	-119.47	52.72	1096	-1.2	-0.7	-0.5	1
6903	1946-01-08	CARIBOO LODGE	BC	1171393	-119.47	52.72	1096	-2.9	-0.9	-2	1
6904	1946-01-14	CARIBOO LODGE	BC	1171393	-119.47	52.72	1096	-2.3	-0.6	-1.7	1
6905	1946-01-16	CARIBOO LODGE	BC	1171393	-119.47	52.72	1096	-3.5	-0.9	-2.6	1
6906	1946-01-17	CARIBOO LODGE	BC	1171393	-119.47	52.72	1096	-0.8	-0.7	-0.1	1
6907	1946-01-20	CARIBOO LODGE	BC	1171393	-119.47	52.72	1096	-9.5	-8.9	-0.6	1
6908	1946-01-27	CARIBOO LODGE	BC	1171393	-119.47	52.72	1096	-9	-6.4	-2.6	1
6909	1946-02-13	CARIBOO LODGE	BC	1171393	-119.47	52.72	1096	-1.2	-0.7	-0.5	1
6910	1946-02-26	CARIBOO LODGE	BC	1171393	-119.47	52.72	1096	-1.3	-0.8	-0.5	1
6911	1946-11-02	CARIBOO LODGE	BC	1171393	-119.47	52.72	1096	-0.8	0.8	-1.6	1
6912	1946-11-18	CARIBOO LODGE	BC	1171393	-119.47	52.72	1096	-17.5	-15.8	-1.7	1
6913	1946-11-28	CARIBOO LODGE	BC	1171393	-119.47	52.72	1096	-2.3	-0.6	-1.7	1
6914	1946-12-01	CARIBOO LODGE	BC	1171393	-119.47	52.72	1096	-5.3	-4.8	-0.5	1
6915	1946-12-02	CARIBOO LODGE	BC	1171393	-119.47	52.72	1096	-1.8	-0.9	-0.9	1
6916	1946-12-03	CARIBOO LODGE	BC	1171393	-119.47	52.72	1096	-0.1	0.1	-0.2	1
6917	1946-12-14	CARIBOO LODGE	BC	1171393	-119.47	52.72	1096	-10.7	-8.9	-1.8	1
6918	1946-12-18	CARIBOO LODGE	BC	1171393	-119.47	52.72	1096	-9.5	-7.6	-1.9	1
6919	1946-12-19	CARIBOO LODGE	BC	1171393	-119.47	52.72	1096	-6.5	-5.8	-0.7	1
6920	1946-12-20	CARIBOO LODGE	BC	1171393	-119.47	52.72	1096	-1.8	-0.9	-0.9	1
6921	1946-12-28	CARIBOO LODGE	BC	1171393	-119.47	52.72	1096	-18	-17	-1	1
6922	1946-12-30	CARIBOO LODGE	BC	1171393	-119.47	52.72	1096	-14.1	-12.4	-1.7	1
6923	1947-01-03	CARIBOO LODGE	BC	1171393	-119.47	52.72	1096	-10.7	-10.4	-0.3	1
6924	1947-01-06	CARIBOO LODGE	BC	1171393	-119.47	52.72	1096	-6.5	-5.8	-0.7	1
6925	1947-01-08	CARIBOO LODGE	BC	1171393	-119.47	52.72	1096	-4.1	-2.2	-1.9	1
6926	1947-01-09	CARIBOO LODGE	BC	1171393	-119.47	52.72	1096	-2.3	-1	-1.3	1
6927	1947-01-11	CARIBOO LODGE	BC	1171393	-119.47	52.72	1096	-2.3	-1	-1.3	1
6928	1947-01-14	CARIBOO LODGE	BC	1171393	-119.47	52.72	1096	-25.3	-19	-6.3	1
6929	1947-01-16	CARIBOO LODGE	BC	1171393	-119.47	52.72	1096	-10.7	-7.6	-3.1	1
6930	1947-01-20	CARIBOO LODGE	BC	1171393	-119.47	52.72	1096	-1.8	-1	-0.8	1
6931	1947-01-21	CARIBOO LODGE	BC	1171393	-119.47	52.72	1096	-1.8	-1.1	-0.7	1
6932	1947-01-29	CARIBOO LODGE	BC	1171393	-119.47	52.72	1096	-24.2	-22.1	-2.1	1
6933	1947-01-31	CARIBOO LODGE	BC	1171393	-119.47	52.72	1096	-28.6	-25.8	-2.8	1
6934	1947-02-01	CARIBOO LODGE	BC	1171393	-119.47	52.72	1096	-17.5	-17.4	-0.1	1
6935	1947-02-03	CARIBOO LODGE	BC	1171393	-119.47	52.72	1096	-13.5	-10.5	-3	1

6936	1947-02-04	CARIBOO LODGE	BC	1171393	-119.47	52.72	1096	-9	-5.3	-3.7	1
6937	1947-02-24	CARIBOO LODGE	BC	1171393	-119.47	52.72	1096	-2.3	-2.2	-0.1	1
6938	1947-02-27	CARIBOO LODGE	BC	1171393	-119.47	52.72	1096	-2.3	-0.8	-1.5	1
6939	1947-02-28	CARIBOO LODGE	BC	1171393	-119.47	52.72	1096	-1.8	-1.4	-0.4	1
6940	1947-03-07	CARIBOO LODGE	BC	1171393	-119.47	52.72	1096	-1.8	-1	-0.8	1
6941	1947-06-18	CARIBOO LODGE	BC	1171393	-119.47	52.72	1096	3.6	4.3	-0.7	1
6942	1947-11-06	CARIBOO LODGE	BC	1171393	-119.47	52.72	1096	-2.9	-1.4	-1.5	1
6943	1947-11-10	CARIBOO LODGE	BC	1171393	-119.47	52.72	1096	-1.2	-1	-0.2	1
6944	1947-11-11	CARIBOO LODGE	BC	1171393	-119.47	52.72	1096	-1.2	-1	-0.2	1
6945	1947-11-12	CARIBOO LODGE	BC	1171393	-119.47	52.72	1096	-1.8	-1.4	-0.4	1
6946	1947-11-21	CARIBOO LODGE	BC	1171393	-119.47	52.72	1096	-10.1	-6.9	-3.2	1
6947	1947-11-22	CARIBOO LODGE	BC	1171393	-119.47	52.72	1096	-7.2	-6.4	-0.8	1
6948	1947-11-23	CARIBOO LODGE	BC	1171393	-119.47	52.72	1096	-3.5	-2.9	-0.6	1
6949	1947-11-24	CARIBOO LODGE	BC	1171393	-119.47	52.72	1096	-1.8	-1	-0.8	1
6950	1947-11-30	CARIBOO LODGE	BC	1171393	-119.47	52.72	1096	-7.2	-6.4	-0.8	1
6951	1947-12-06	CARIBOO LODGE	BC	1171393	-119.47	52.72	1096	-5.9	-4.8	-1.1	1
6952	1947-12-12	CARIBOO LODGE	BC	1171393	-119.47	52.72	1096	-5.3	-2.2	-3.1	1
6953	1947-12-16	CARIBOO LODGE	BC	1171393	-119.47	52.72	1096	-6.5	-3.7	-2.8	1
6954	1947-12-20	CARIBOO LODGE	BC	1171393	-119.47	52.72	1096	-2.9	-1.4	-1.5	1
6955	1947-12-24	CARIBOO LODGE	BC	1171393	-119.47	52.72	1096	-3.5	-1.1	-2.4	1
6956	1947-12-30	CARIBOO LODGE	BC	1171393	-119.47	52.72	1096	-9.5	-6.4	-3.1	1
6957	1947-12-31	CARIBOO LODGE	BC	1171393	-119.47	52.72	1096	-4.7	-3.7	-1	1
6958	1948-01-05	CARIBOO LODGE	BC	1171393	-119.47	52.72	1096	-4.1	-2.9	-1.2	1
6959	1948-01-17	CARIBOO LODGE	BC	1171393	-119.47	52.72	1096	-5.3	-4.8	-0.5	1
6960	1948-01-21	CARIBOO LODGE	BC	1171393	-119.47	52.72	1096	-2.9	-1	-1.9	1
6961	1948-01-22	CARIBOO LODGE	BC	1171393	-119.47	52.72	1096	-3.5	-2.1	-1.4	1
6962	1948-01-27	CARIBOO LODGE	BC	1171393	-119.47	52.72	1096	-7.2	-6.4	-0.8	1
6963	1948-01-28	CARIBOO LODGE	BC	1171393	-119.47	52.72	1096	-6.5	-6.4	-0.1	1
6964	1948-02-12	CARIBOO LODGE	BC	1171393	-119.47	52.72	1096	-7.7	-6.4	-1.3	1
6965	1948-03-12	CARIBOO LODGE	BC	1171393	-119.47	52.72	1096	-3.5	-1.1	-2.4	1
6966	1948-03-13	CARIBOO LODGE	BC	1171393	-119.47	52.72	1096	-1.2	-1	-0.2	1
6967	1948-03-20	CARIBOO LODGE	BC	1171393	-119.47	52.72	1096	-2.9	-1.1	-1.8	1
6968	1948-04-12	CARIBOO LODGE	BC	1171393	-119.47	52.72	1096	-0.8	0.1	-0.9	1
6969	1948-11-09	CARIBOO LODGE	BC	1171393	-119.47	52.72	1096	-1.2	-0.9	-0.3	1

6970	1948-11-10	CARIBOO LODGE	BC	1171393	-119.47	52.72	1096	-1.2	-0.9	-0.3	1
6971	1948-11-11	CARIBOO LODGE	BC	1171393	-119.47	52.72	1096	-2.3	-0.9	-1.4	1
6972	1948-11-18	CARIBOO LODGE	BC	1171393	-119.47	52.72	1096	-2.9	-0.9	-2	1
6973	1948-11-28	CARIBOO LODGE	BC	1171393	-119.47	52.72	1096	-5.3	-4.2	-1.1	1
6974	1948-11-29	CARIBOO LODGE	BC	1171393	-119.47	52.72	1096	-5.3	-3.6	-1.7	1
6975	1948-11-30	CARIBOO LODGE	BC	1171393	-119.47	52.72	1096	-2.9	-1.4	-1.5	1
6976	1948-12-19	CARIBOO LODGE	BC	1171393	-119.47	52.72	1096	-10.7	-8.2	-2.5	1
6977	1948-12-28	CARIBOO LODGE	BC	1171393	-119.47	52.72	1096	-12.4	-9.8	-2.6	1
6978	1948-12-30	CARIBOO LODGE	BC	1171393	-119.47	52.72	1096	-7.2	-4.8	-2.4	1
6979	1949-01-10	CARIBOO LODGE	BC	1171393	-119.47	52.72	1096	-20.3	-16.7	-3.6	1
6980	1949-01-16	CARIBOO LODGE	BC	1171393	-119.47	52.72	1096	-7.2	-6.4	-0.8	1
6981	1949-01-20	CARIBOO LODGE	BC	1171393	-119.47	52.72	1096	-20.8	-16.2	-4.6	1
6982	1949-02-20	CARIBOO LODGE	BC	1171393	-119.47	52.72	1096	-12.9	-9.8	-3.1	1
6983	1949-02-21	CARIBOO LODGE	BC	1171393	-119.47	52.72	1096	-5.9	-3.6	-2.3	1
6984	1949-03-20	CARIBOO LODGE	BC	1171393	-119.47	52.72	1096	0.4	0.8	-0.4	1
6985	1949-11-23	CARIBOO LODGE	BC	1171393	-119.47	52.72	1096	-1.8	-1.1	-0.7	1
6986	1949-11-30	CARIBOO LODGE	BC	1171393	-119.47	52.72	1096	-2.3	0.1	-2.4	1
6987	1949-12-04	CARIBOO LODGE	BC	1171393	-119.47	52.72	1096	-7.2	-3.7	-3.5	1
6988	1949-12-11	CARIBOO LODGE	BC	1171393	-119.47	52.72	1096	-11.8	-11.3	-0.5	1
6989	1949-12-14	CARIBOO LODGE	BC	1171393	-119.47	52.72	1096	-12.9	-11.8	-1.1	1
6990	1949-12-17	CARIBOO LODGE	BC	1171393	-119.47	52.72	1096	-17.5	-16.5	-1	1
6991	1949-12-28	CARIBOO LODGE	BC	1171393	-119.47	52.72	1096	-23	-17.8	-5.2	1
6992	1949-12-30	CARIBOO LODGE	BC	1171393	-119.47	52.72	1096	-21.9	-17.8	-4.1	1
6993	1950-01-05	CARIBOO LODGE	BC	1171393	-119.47	52.72	1096	-17.5	-16.5	-1	1
6994	1950-01-09	CARIBOO LODGE	BC	1171393	-119.47	52.72	1096	-23	-19	-4	1
6995	1950-01-11	CARIBOO LODGE	BC	1171393	-119.47	52.72	1096	-23.6	-19.5	-4.1	1
6996	1950-01-21	CARIBOO LODGE	BC	1171393	-119.47	52.72	1096	-17.5	-14.7	-2.8	1
6997	1950-01-22	CARIBOO LODGE	BC	1171393	-119.47	52.72	1096	-17.5	-15.9	-1.6	1
6998	1950-01-23	CARIBOO LODGE	BC	1171393	-119.47	52.72	1096	-28.6	-25.7	-2.9	1
6999	1950-01-30	CARIBOO LODGE	BC	1171393	-119.47	52.72	1096	-23	-22.6	-0.4	1
7000	1950-02-02	CARIBOO LODGE	BC	1171393	-119.47	52.72	1096	-15.3	-15.2	-0.1	1
7001	1950-02-03	CARIBOO LODGE	BC	1171393	-119.47	52.72	1096	-17.5	-15	-2.5	1
7002	1950-02-04	CARIBOO LODGE	BC	1171393	-119.47	52.72	1096	-10.1	-8.3	-1.8	1
7003	1950-02-12	CARIBOO LODGE	BC	1171393	-119.47	52.72	1096	-0.8	-0.7	-0.1	1

7004	1950-02-14	CARIBOO LODGE	BC	1171393	-119.47	52.72	1096	-0.1	1.5	-1.6	1
7005	1950-02-15	CARIBOO LODGE	BC	1171393	-119.47	52.72	1096	-0.1	0.2	-0.3	1
7006	1950-03-02	CARIBOO LODGE	BC	1171393	-119.47	52.72	1096	-2.3	-0.7	-1.6	1
7007	1950-10-25	CARIBOO LODGE	BC	1171393	-119.47	52.72	1096	-1.3	-0.6	-0.7	1
7008	1950-10-31	CARIBOO LODGE	BC	1171393	-119.47	52.72	1096	-2.9	-2.3	-0.6	1
7009	1950-11-02	CARIBOO LODGE	BC	1171393	-119.47	52.72	1096	-1.2	-0.6	-0.6	1
7010	1950-11-25	CARIBOO LODGE	BC	1171393	-119.47	52.72	1096	-1.2	-0.6	-0.6	1
7011	1950-11-26	CARIBOO LODGE	BC	1171393	-119.47	52.72	1096	1.1	1.5	-0.4	1
7012	1950-11-27	CARIBOO LODGE	BC	1171393	-119.47	52.72	1096	1.8	1.9	-0.1	1
7013	1950-12-06	CARIBOO LODGE	BC	1171393	-119.47	52.72	1096	-4.7	-4.2	-0.5	1
7014	1950-12-07	CARIBOO LODGE	BC	1171393	-119.47	52.72	1096	-7.2	-6.4	-0.8	1
7015	1950-12-09	CARIBOO LODGE	BC	1171393	-119.47	52.72	1096	-1.2	-0.7	-0.5	1
7016	1950-12-11	CARIBOO LODGE	BC	1171393	-119.47	52.72	1096	-2.3	-0.8	-1.5	1
7017	1950-12-13	CARIBOO LODGE	BC	1171393	-119.47	52.72	1096	-1.8	-1.4	-0.4	1
7018	1950-12-17	CARIBOO LODGE	BC	1171393	-119.47	52.72	1096	-2.3	-1.4	-0.9	1
7019	1950-12-22	CARIBOO LODGE	BC	1171393	-119.47	52.72	1096	0.4	1.5	-1.1	1
7020	1950-12-23	CARIBOO LODGE	BC	1171393	-119.47	52.72	1096	-1.8	-0.6	-1.2	1
7021	1950-12-24	CARIBOO LODGE	BC	1171393	-119.47	52.72	1096	-0.1	0	-0.1	1
7022	1951-01-07	CARIBOO LODGE	BC	1171393	-119.47	52.72	1096	-7.7	-6.9	-0.8	1
7023	1951-01-08	CARIBOO LODGE	BC	1171393	-119.47	52.72	1096	-5.9	-4.8	-1.1	1
7024	1951-01-22	CARIBOO LODGE	BC	1171393	-119.47	52.72	1096	-5.3	-3.6	-1.7	1
7025	1951-02-01	CARIBOO LODGE	BC	1171393	-119.47	52.72	1096	-15.8	-13.8	-2	1
7026	1951-02-14	CARIBOO LODGE	BC	1171393	-119.47	52.72	1096	-4.7	-3.6	-1.1	1
7027	1951-03-12	CARIBOO LODGE	BC	1171393	-119.47	52.72	1096	-4.7	-2.9	-1.8	1
7028	1951-10-23	CARIBOO LODGE	BC	1171393	-119.47	52.72	1096	-5.9	-5.3	-0.6	1
7029	1951-11-03	CARIBOO LODGE	BC	1171393	-119.47	52.72	1096	-3.5	-1.4	-2.1	1
7030	1951-11-12	CARIBOO LODGE	BC	1171393	-119.47	52.72	1096	-1.2	-0.7	-0.5	1
7031	1951-11-17	CARIBOO LODGE	BC	1171393	-119.47	52.72	1096	-4	-3.7	-0.3	1
7032	1951-11-18	CARIBOO LODGE	BC	1171393	-119.47	52.72	1096	-0.8	-0.6	-0.2	1
7033	1951-12-02	CARIBOO LODGE	BC	1171393	-119.47	52.72	1096	-2.9	-2.3	-0.6	1
7034	1951-12-08	CARIBOO LODGE	BC	1171393	-119.47	52.72	1096	-7.2	-6.4	-0.8	1
7035	1951-12-09	CARIBOO LODGE	BC	1171393	-119.47	52.72	1096	-7.7	-7.6	-0.1	1
7036	1951-12-20	CARIBOO LODGE	BC	1171393	-119.47	52.72	1096	-19.2	-17.4	-1.8	1
7037	1952-01-01	CARIBOO LODGE	BC	1171393	-119.47	52.72	1096	-23	-19.7	-3.3	1

7038	1952-01-02	CARIBOO LODGE	BC	1171393	-119.47	52.72	1096	-15.8	-14.1	-1.7	1
7039	1952-01-05	CARIBOO LODGE	BC	1171393	-119.47	52.72	1096	-8.3	-6.4	-1.9	1
7040	1952-01-08	CARIBOO LODGE	BC	1171393	-119.47	52.72	1096	-7.2	-6.4	-0.8	1
7041	1952-01-21	CARIBOO LODGE	BC	1171393	-119.47	52.72	1096	-26.4	-25.2	-1.2	1
7042	1952-01-22	CARIBOO LODGE	BC	1171393	-119.47	52.72	1096	-23.6	-22.1	-1.5	1
7043	1952-01-23	CARIBOO LODGE	BC	1171393	-119.47	52.72	1096	-19.2	-17.9	-1.3	1
7044	1952-01-27	CARIBOO LODGE	BC	1171393	-119.47	52.72	1096	-0.8	0.9	-1.7	1
7045	1952-02-05	CARIBOO LODGE	BC	1171393	-119.47	52.72	1096	-2.3	-0.6	-1.7	1
7046	1952-02-08	CARIBOO LODGE	BC	1171393	-119.47	52.72	1096	-1.2	-0.6	-0.6	1
7047	1952-03-17	CARIBOO LODGE	BC	1171393	-119.47	52.72	1096	-1.3	-1.1	-0.2	1
7048	1952-06-04	CARIBOO LODGE	BC	1171393	-119.47	52.72	1096	8.7	8.9	-0.2	1
7049	1952-11-02	CARIBOO LODGE	BC	1171393	-119.47	52.72	1096	-0.8	-0.6	-0.2	1
7050	1952-11-16	CARIBOO LODGE	BC	1171393	-119.47	52.72	1096	-3.5	-1.4	-2.1	1
7051	1952-11-22	CARIBOO LODGE	BC	1171393	-119.47	52.72	1096	-4.1	-1.4	-2.7	1
7052	1952-11-23	CARIBOO LODGE	BC	1171393	-119.47	52.72	1096	-4	-3.7	-0.3	1
7053	1952-11-24	CARIBOO LODGE	BC	1171393	-119.47	52.72	1096	-5.3	-4.8	-0.5	1
7054	1952-11-26	CARIBOO LODGE	BC	1171393	-119.47	52.72	1096	-5.3	-4.8	-0.5	1
7055	1952-12-01	CARIBOO LODGE	BC	1171393	-119.47	52.72	1096	-4.7	-3.7	-1	1
7056	1952-12-02	CARIBOO LODGE	BC	1171393	-119.47	52.72	1096	-2.9	-2.3	-0.6	1
7057	1952-12-15	CARIBOO LODGE	BC	1171393	-119.47	52.72	1096	-1.8	-1	-0.8	1
7058	1952-12-16	CARIBOO LODGE	BC	1171393	-119.47	52.72	1096	-3.4	-2.9	-0.5	1
7059	1952-12-17	CARIBOO LODGE	BC	1171393	-119.47	52.72	1096	-9.7	-7.4	-2.3	1
7060	1952-12-25	CARIBOO LODGE	BC	1171393	-119.47	52.72	1096	-10.1	-9	-1.1	1
7061	1952-12-26	CARIBOO LODGE	BC	1171393	-119.47	52.72	1096	-7.9	-6.9	-1	1
7062	1952-12-27	CARIBOO LODGE	BC	1171393	-119.47	52.72	1096	-7.9	-7.4	-0.5	1
7063	1953-01-02	CARIBOO LODGE	BC	1171393	-119.47	52.72	1096	-3.4	-2.9	-0.5	1
7064	1953-01-03	CARIBOO LODGE	BC	1171393	-119.47	52.72	1096	-1.9	-1.6	-0.3	1
7065	1953-01-07	CARIBOO LODGE	BC	1171393	-119.47	52.72	1096	-24	-18.9	-5.1	1
7066	1953-01-08	CARIBOO LODGE	BC	1171393	-119.47	52.72	1096	-24.6	-24.2	-0.4	1
7067	1953-01-12	CARIBOO LODGE	BC	1171393	-119.47	52.72	1096	-29.6	-28.1	-1.5	1
7068	1953-01-28	CARIBOO LODGE	BC	1171393	-119.47	52.72	1096	-2.9	-1.6	-1.3	1
7069	1953-01-31	CARIBOO LODGE	BC	1171393	-119.47	52.72	1096	0.8	2.2	-1.4	1
7070	1953-02-03	CARIBOO LODGE	BC	1171393	-119.47	52.72	1096	0.2	2.2	-2	1
7071	1953-02-06	CARIBOO LODGE	BC	1171393	-119.47	52.72	1096	-1.4	-0.6	-0.8	1

7072	1953-03-11	CARIBOO LODGE	BC	1171393	-119.47	52.72	1096	-1	-0.1	-0.9	1
7073	1953-10-26	CARIBOO LODGE	BC	1171393	-119.47	52.72	1096	1.3	1.6	-0.3	1
7074	1953-10-28	CARIBOO LODGE	BC	1171393	-119.47	52.72	1096	0.8	2.9	-2.1	1
7075	1953-11-01	CARIBOO LODGE	BC	1171393	-119.47	52.72	1096	-1	0.8	-1.8	1
7076	1953-11-04	CARIBOO LODGE	BC	1171393	-119.47	52.72	1096	-2	-0.1	-1.9	1
7077	1953-11-05	CARIBOO LODGE	BC	1171393	-119.47	52.72	1096	-1	-0.6	-0.4	1
7078	1953-11-06	CARIBOO LODGE	BC	1171393	-119.47	52.72	1096	-1.4	0.8	-2.2	1
7079	1953-11-11	CARIBOO LODGE	BC	1171393	-119.47	52.72	1096	-1	-0.6	-0.4	1
7080	1953-11-12	CARIBOO LODGE	BC	1171393	-119.47	52.72	1096	0.2	1.6	-1.4	1
7081	1953-11-13	CARIBOO LODGE	BC	1171393	-119.47	52.72	1096	2.9	3.5	-0.6	1
7082	1953-11-14	CARIBOO LODGE	BC	1171393	-119.47	52.72	1096	4.3	4.5	-0.2	1
7083	1953-11-15	CARIBOO LODGE	BC	1171393	-119.47	52.72	1096	6.6	7.5	-0.9	1
7084	1953-11-27	CARIBOO LODGE	BC	1171393	-119.47	52.72	1096	0.8	1.5	-0.7	1
7085	1953-11-28	CARIBOO LODGE	BC	1171393	-119.47	52.72	1096	-2.4	-1.1	-1.3	1
7086	1953-11-29	CARIBOO LODGE	BC	1171393	-119.47	52.72	1096	-1	-0.6	-0.4	1
7087	1953-11-30	CARIBOO LODGE	BC	1171393	-119.47	52.72	1096	-2	-1.1	-0.9	1
7088	1953-12-01	CARIBOO LODGE	BC	1171393	-119.47	52.72	1096	-1.5	-0.4	-1.1	1
7089	1953-12-03	CARIBOO LODGE	BC	1171393	-119.47	52.72	1096	-3.4	-2.2	-1.2	1
7090	1953-12-04	CARIBOO LODGE	BC	1171393	-119.47	52.72	1096	-2.9	-1.1	-1.8	1
7091	1953-12-05	CARIBOO LODGE	BC	1171393	-119.47	52.72	1096	-3.9	-1.1	-2.8	1
7092	1953-12-06	CARIBOO LODGE	BC	1171393	-119.47	52.72	1096	-6.8	-4.7	-2.1	1
7093	1953-12-22	CARIBOO LODGE	BC	1171393	-119.47	52.72	1096	-9.1	-7.4	-1.7	1
7094	1954-01-01	CARIBOO LODGE	BC	1171393	-119.47	52.72	1096	-11.9	-10.4	-1.5	1
7095	1954-01-02	CARIBOO LODGE	BC	1171393	-119.47	52.72	1096	-9.7	-9.3	-0.4	1
7096	1954-01-04	CARIBOO LODGE	BC	1171393	-119.47	52.72	1096	-10.8	-9.4	-1.4	1
7097	1954-01-05	CARIBOO LODGE	BC	1171393	-119.47	52.72	1096	-12.3	-10.3	-2	1
7098	1954-01-08	CARIBOO LODGE	BC	1171393	-119.47	52.72	1096	-20.7	-20.5	-0.2	1
7099	1954-01-09	CARIBOO LODGE	BC	1171393	-119.47	52.72	1096	-17.3	-15.3	-2	1
7100	1954-01-15	CARIBOO LODGE	BC	1171393	-119.47	52.72	1096	-20.7	-18.3	-2.4	1
7101	1954-01-21	CARIBOO LODGE	BC	1171393	-119.47	52.72	1096	-22.9	-20.5	-2.4	1
7102	1954-01-22	CARIBOO LODGE	BC	1171393	-119.47	52.72	1096	-26.2	-25.9	-0.3	1
7103	1954-01-24	CARIBOO LODGE	BC	1171393	-119.47	52.72	1096	-24	-22.7	-1.3	1
7104	1954-01-26	CARIBOO LODGE	BC	1171393	-119.47	52.72	1096	-19.6	-17.3	-2.3	1
7105	1954-02-01	CARIBOO LODGE	BC	1171393	-119.47	52.72	1096	-3.4	-2.3	-1.1	1

7106	1954-02-02	CARIBOO LODGE	BC	1171393	-119.47	52.72	1096	-1.5	0.7	-2.2	1
7107	1954-02-03	CARIBOO LODGE	BC	1171393	-119.47	52.72	1096	0.8	1.5	-0.7	1
7108	1954-02-05	CARIBOO LODGE	BC	1171393	-119.47	52.72	1096	2.5	3	-0.5	1
7109	1954-02-06	CARIBOO LODGE	BC	1171393	-119.47	52.72	1096	1.3	1.5	-0.2	1
7110	1954-02-12	CARIBOO LODGE	BC	1171393	-119.47	52.72	1096	-12.3	-8.4	-3.9	1
7111	1954-02-17	CARIBOO LODGE	BC	1171393	-119.47	52.72	1096	-7.3	-6.4	-0.9	1
7112	1954-05-11	CARIBOO LODGE	BC	1171393	-119.47	52.72	1096	4.3	4.4	-0.1	1
7113	1954-05-24	CARIBOO LODGE	BC	1171393	-119.47	52.72	1096	6.5	6.9	-0.4	1
7114	1954-05-25	CARIBOO LODGE	BC	1171393	-119.47	52.72	1096	5.9	6.4	-0.5	1
7115	1954-06-05	CARIBOO LODGE	BC	1171393	-119.47	52.72	1096	5.9	6.8	-0.9	1
7116	1954-10-03	CARIBOO LODGE	BC	1171393	-119.47	52.72	1096	-5.1	-3.5	-1.6	1
7117	1954-10-12	CARIBOO LODGE	BC	1171393	-119.47	52.72	1096	2.4	5	-2.6	1
7118	1954-10-13	CARIBOO LODGE	BC	1171393	-119.47	52.72	1096	2.4	3.8	-1.4	1
7119	1954-10-15	CARIBOO LODGE	BC	1171393	-119.47	52.72	1096	3.4	5	-1.6	1
7120	1954-10-16	CARIBOO LODGE	BC	1171393	-119.47	52.72	1096	3.4	3.8	-0.4	1
7121	1954-10-20	CARIBOO LODGE	BC	1171393	-119.47	52.72	1096	3.4	3.9	-0.5	1
7122	1954-10-21	CARIBOO LODGE	BC	1171393	-119.47	52.72	1096	2.9	3.9	-1	1
7123	1954-12-29	CARIBOO LODGE	BC	1171393	-119.47	52.72	1096	-26.2	-22.1	-4.1	1
7124	1954-12-31	CARIBOO LODGE	BC	1171393	-119.47	52.72	1096	-13.5	-11.3	-2.2	1
7125	1955-02-16	CARIBOO LODGE	BC	1171393	-119.47	52.72	1096	-2.4	-0.9	-1.5	1
7126	1955-10-30	CARIBOO LODGE	BC	1171393	-119.47	52.72	1096	-2.4	-0.4	-2	1
7127	1955-11-08	CARIBOO LODGE	BC	1171393	-119.47	52.72	1096	-0.4	-0.1	-0.3	1
7128	1955-11-10	CARIBOO LODGE	BC	1171393	-119.47	52.72	1096	-3.4	-2.2	-1.2	1
7129	1955-11-25	CARIBOO LODGE	BC	1171393	-119.47	52.72	1096	-19.6	-17.9	-1.7	1
7130	1955-12-08	CARIBOO LODGE	BC	1171393	-119.47	52.72	1096	-3.9	-2.2	-1.7	1
7131	1955-12-11	CARIBOO LODGE	BC	1171393	-119.47	52.72	1096	-4.5	-2.2	-2.3	1
7132	1955-12-27	CARIBOO LODGE	BC	1171393	-119.47	52.72	1096	-16.2	-13.7	-2.5	1
7133	1956-01-13	CARIBOO LODGE	BC	1171393	-119.47	52.72	1096	-3.9	-0.7	-3.2	1
7134	1956-01-14	CARIBOO LODGE	BC	1171393	-119.47	52.72	1096	-14.6	-12.8	-1.8	1
7135	1956-01-19	CARIBOO LODGE	BC	1171393	-119.47	52.72	1096	-2.4	-2.2	-0.2	1
7136	1956-02-12	CARIBOO LODGE	BC	1171393	-119.47	52.72	1096	-9.1	-7.9	-1.2	1
7137	1956-02-21	CARIBOO LODGE	BC	1171393	-119.47	52.72	1096	-12.3	-11.8	-0.5	1
7138	1956-05-11	CARIBOO LODGE	BC	1171393	-119.47	52.72	1096	4.3	5	-0.7	1
7139	1956-09-25	CARIBOO LODGE	BC	1171393	-119.47	52.72	1096	7.8	8.1	-0.3	1

7140	1956-10-27	CARIBOO LODGE	BC	1171393	-119.47	52.72	1096	-5.1	-5	-0.1	1
7141	1956-11-03	CARIBOO LODGE	BC	1171393	-119.47	52.72	1096	-1.4	-0.1	-1.3	1
7142	1956-11-09	CARIBOO LODGE	BC	1171393	-119.47	52.72	1096	1.9	2.7	-0.8	1
7143	1956-11-10	CARIBOO LODGE	BC	1171393	-119.47	52.72	1096	0.8	2.2	-1.4	1
7144	1956-11-12	CARIBOO LODGE	BC	1171393	-119.47	52.72	1096	0.2	0.7	-0.5	1
7145	1956-11-17	CARIBOO LODGE	BC	1171393	-119.47	52.72	1096	-2.4	-2.2	-0.2	1
7146	1956-12-02	CARIBOO LODGE	BC	1171393	-119.47	52.72	1096	-5.1	-4.7	-0.4	1
7147	1956-12-03	CARIBOO LODGE	BC	1171393	-119.47	52.72	1096	-16.8	-15.3	-1.5	1
7148	1956-12-10	CARIBOO LODGE	BC	1171393	-119.47	52.72	1096	-8.6	-7.4	-1.2	1
7149	1956-12-14	CARIBOO LODGE	BC	1171393	-119.47	52.72	1096	-4.5	-2.9	-1.6	1
7150	1956-12-20	CARIBOO LODGE	BC	1171393	-119.47	52.72	1096	-2.4	0.6	-3	1
7151	1956-12-25	CARIBOO LODGE	BC	1171393	-119.47	52.72	1096	-1.4	2.2	-3.6	1
7152	1956-12-26	CARIBOO LODGE	BC	1171393	-119.47	52.72	1096	-1	0.6	-1.6	1
7153	1956-12-27	CARIBOO LODGE	BC	1171393	-119.47	52.72	1096	-2	1.5	-3.5	1
7154	1956-12-29	CARIBOO LODGE	BC	1171393	-119.47	52.72	1096	-2.4	-0.8	-1.6	1
7155	1956-12-31	CARIBOO LODGE	BC	1171393	-119.47	52.72	1096	-2.9	-1.6	-1.3	1
7156	1957-01-01	CARIBOO LODGE	BC	1171393	-119.47	52.72	1096	-2.9	-0.1	-2.8	1
7157	1957-01-02	CARIBOO LODGE	BC	1171393	-119.47	52.72	1096	-3.9	-1.6	-2.3	1
7158	1957-01-07	CARIBOO LODGE	BC	1171393	-119.47	52.72	1096	-6.2	-4.7	-1.5	1
7159	1957-01-19	CARIBOO LODGE	BC	1171393	-119.47	52.72	1096	-14.6	-13.8	-0.8	1
7160	1957-01-30	CARIBOO LODGE	BC	1171393	-119.47	52.72	1096	-11.9	-9.3	-2.6	1
7161	1957-02-11	CARIBOO LODGE	BC	1171393	-119.47	52.72	1096	-1.9	-0.6	-1.3	1
7162	1957-02-12	CARIBOO LODGE	BC	1171393	-119.47	52.72	1096	-1.4	-1	-0.4	1
7163	1957-02-14	CARIBOO LODGE	BC	1171393	-119.47	52.72	1096	-1.4	-1	-0.4	1
7164	1957-03-20	CARIBOO LODGE	BC	1171393	-119.47	52.72	1096	1.3	3.5	-2.2	1
7165	1957-10-04	CARIBOO LODGE	BC	1171393	-119.47	52.72	1096	-4.5	-3	-1.5	1
7166	1957-10-30	CARIBOO LODGE	BC	1171393	-119.47	52.72	1096	4.3	5.1	-0.8	1
7167	1957-11-11	CARIBOO LODGE	BC	1171393	-119.47	52.72	1096	1.9	2.2	-0.3	1
7168	1957-11-12	CARIBOO LODGE	BC	1171393	-119.47	52.72	1096	1.3	2.2	-0.9	1
7169	1957-11-23	CARIBOO LODGE	BC	1171393	-119.47	52.72	1096	-0.4	0.6	-1	1
7170	1957-12-04	CARIBOO LODGE	BC	1171393	-119.47	52.72	1096	-1.4	-0.5	-0.9	1
7171	1957-12-10	CARIBOO LODGE	BC	1171393	-119.47	52.72	1096	-1	-0.7	-0.3	1
7172	1957-12-12	CARIBOO LODGE	BC	1171393	-119.47	52.72	1096	-3.9	-2.9	-1	1
7173	1957-12-18	CARIBOO LODGE	BC	1171393	-119.47	52.72	1096	-2.9	-0.5	-2.4	1

7174	1957-12-23	CARIBOO LODGE	BC	1171393	-119.47	52.72	1096	-3.9	-3	-0.9	1
7175	1958-01-07	CARIBOO LODGE	BC	1171393	-119.47	52.72	1096	-1.4	-1	-0.4	1
7176	1958-01-08	CARIBOO LODGE	BC	1171393	-119.47	52.72	1096	-2.4	-1.6	-0.8	1
7177	1958-01-09	CARIBOO LODGE	BC	1171393	-119.47	52.72	1096	-5.1	-4.6	-0.5	1
7178	1958-01-14	CARIBOO LODGE	BC	1171393	-119.47	52.72	1096	-1	-0.6	-0.4	1
7179	1958-01-15	CARIBOO LODGE	BC	1171393	-119.47	52.72	1096	-2.4	-0.5	-1.9	1
7180	1958-01-17	CARIBOO LODGE	BC	1171393	-119.47	52.72	1096	-1	-0.9	-0.1	1
7181	1958-01-21	CARIBOO LODGE	BC	1171393	-119.47	52.72	1096	-1.4	-0.5	-0.9	1
7182	1958-01-24	CARIBOO LODGE	BC	1171393	-119.47	52.72	1096	-5.1	-4.1	-1	1
7183	1958-02-18	CARIBOO LODGE	BC	1171393	-119.47	52.72	1096	0.2	0.5	-0.3	1
7184	1958-02-19	CARIBOO LODGE	BC	1171393	-119.47	52.72	1096	1.3	2.7	-1.4	1
7185	1958-10-31	CARIBOO LODGE	BC	1171393	-119.47	52.72	1096	3.8	4.4	-0.6	1
7186	1958-11-12	CARIBOO LODGE	BC	1171393	-119.47	52.72	1096	-2	-1.1	-0.9	1
7187	1958-11-18	CARIBOO LODGE	BC	1171393	-119.47	52.72	1096	-7.9	-5.9	-2	1
7188	1958-11-21	CARIBOO LODGE	BC	1171393	-119.47	52.72	1096	-3.4	-1.1	-2.3	1
7189	1958-11-22	CARIBOO LODGE	BC	1171393	-119.47	52.72	1096	-3.9	-1.1	-2.8	1
7190	1958-12-01	CARIBOO LODGE	BC	1171393	-119.47	52.72	1096	-1	0.8	-1.8	1
7191	1958-12-02	CARIBOO LODGE	BC	1171393	-119.47	52.72	1096	0.8	2.2	-1.4	1
7192	1958-12-03	CARIBOO LODGE	BC	1171393	-119.47	52.72	1096	-3.4	-1.1	-2.3	1
7193	1958-12-04	CARIBOO LODGE	BC	1171393	-119.47	52.72	1096	-15.1	-10.3	-4.8	1
7194	1958-12-10	CARIBOO LODGE	BC	1171393	-119.47	52.72	1096	-7.9	-7.4	-0.5	1
7195	1958-12-12	CARIBOO LODGE	BC	1171393	-119.47	52.72	1096	-6.8	-5.9	-0.9	1
7196	1958-12-17	CARIBOO LODGE	BC	1171393	-119.47	52.72	1096	-2.4	-0.5	-1.9	1
7197	1958-12-18	CARIBOO LODGE	BC	1171393	-119.47	52.72	1096	-1	-0.6	-0.4	1
7198	1958-12-21	CARIBOO LODGE	BC	1171393	-119.47	52.72	1096	-2.9	-1.1	-1.8	1
7199	1958-12-22	CARIBOO LODGE	BC	1171393	-119.47	52.72	1096	-2	-1.6	-0.4	1
7200	1958-12-26	CARIBOO LODGE	BC	1171393	-119.47	52.72	1096	-2.9	-2.2	-0.7	1
7201	1959-01-09	CARIBOO LODGE	BC	1171393	-119.47	52.72	1096	0.2	0.9	-0.7	1
7202	1959-01-10	CARIBOO LODGE	BC	1171393	-119.47	52.72	1096	-1	0.8	-1.8	1
7203	1959-01-11	CARIBOO LODGE	BC	1171393	-119.47	52.72	1096	-2	-1.6	-0.4	1
7204	1959-01-13	CARIBOO LODGE	BC	1171393	-119.47	52.72	1096	-1	-0.1	-0.9	1
7205	1959-01-23	CARIBOO LODGE	BC	1171393	-119.47	52.72	1096	-3.4	-2.2	-1.2	1
7206	1959-01-24	CARIBOO LODGE	BC	1171393	-119.47	52.72	1096	-2.9	-1.1	-1.8	1
7207	1959-01-25	CARIBOO LODGE	BC	1171393	-119.47	52.72	1096	-2.4	-0.6	-1.8	1

7208	1959-02-04	CARIBOO LODGE	BC	1171393	-119.47	52.72	1096	-3.4	-3	-0.4	1
7209	1959-02-06	CARIBOO LODGE	BC	1171393	-119.47	52.72	1096	-9.7	-8.9	-0.8	1
7210	1959-03-17	CARIBOO LODGE	BC	1171393	-119.47	52.72	1096	3.8	4.4	-0.6	1
7211	1959-04-22	CARIBOO LODGE	BC	1171393	-119.47	52.72	1096	2.5	3.4	-0.9	1
7212	1959-08-27	CARIBOO LODGE	BC	1171393	-119.47	52.72	1096	5.4	7.4	-2	1
7213	1959-10-30	CARIBOO LODGE	BC	1171393	-119.47	52.72	1096	3.4	4.5	-1.1	1
7214	1959-10-31	CARIBOO LODGE	BC	1171393	-119.47	52.72	1096	2.5	2.9	-0.4	1
7215	1959-11-14	CARIBOO LODGE	BC	1171393	-119.47	52.72	1096	-15.1	-10.8	-4.3	1
7216	1959-12-03	CARIBOO LODGE	BC	1171393	-119.47	52.72	1096	-5.1	-4.6	-0.5	1
7217	1959-12-05	CARIBOO LODGE	BC	1171393	-119.47	52.72	1096	-2.9	-2.2	-0.7	1
7218	1959-12-14	CARIBOO LODGE	BC	1171393	-119.47	52.72	1096	-2.9	-2.2	-0.7	1
7219	1959-12-15	CARIBOO LODGE	BC	1171393	-119.47	52.72	1096	-2.4	-0.5	-1.9	1
7220	1959-12-17	CARIBOO LODGE	BC	1171393	-119.47	52.72	1096	-15.1	-12.2	-2.9	1
7221	1959-12-18	CARIBOO LODGE	BC	1171393	-119.47	52.72	1096	-9.7	-7.8	-1.9	1
7222	1959-12-19	CARIBOO LODGE	BC	1171393	-119.47	52.72	1096	-7.3	-5.4	-1.9	1
7223	1959-12-20	CARIBOO LODGE	BC	1171393	-119.47	52.72	1096	-6.8	-4.6	-2.2	1
7224	1959-12-21	CARIBOO LODGE	BC	1171393	-119.47	52.72	1096	-6.2	-5	-1.2	1
7225	1959-12-22	CARIBOO LODGE	BC	1171393	-119.47	52.72	1096	-9.7	-6.4	-3.3	1
7226	1959-12-23	CARIBOO LODGE	BC	1171393	-119.47	52.72	1096	-9.1	-7.8	-1.3	1
7227	1959-12-24	CARIBOO LODGE	BC	1171393	-119.47	52.72	1096	-6.8	-5.5	-1.3	1
7228	1959-12-25	CARIBOO LODGE	BC	1171393	-119.47	52.72	1096	-10.1	-9.3	-0.8	1
7229	1959-12-27	CARIBOO LODGE	BC	1171393	-119.47	52.72	1096	-12.4	-10.4	-2	1
7230	1959-12-28	CARIBOO LODGE	BC	1171393	-119.47	52.72	1096	-14	-11.2	-2.8	1
7231	1959-12-29	CARIBOO LODGE	BC	1171393	-119.47	52.72	1096	-12.3	-9.9	-2.4	1
7232	1959-12-30	CARIBOO LODGE	BC	1171393	-119.47	52.72	1096	-9.1	-7.8	-1.3	1
7233	1960-01-04	CARIBOO LODGE	BC	1171393	-119.47	52.72	1096	-10.8	-10.4	-0.4	1
7234	1960-01-15	CARIBOO LODGE	BC	1171393	-119.47	52.72	1096	-7.3	-6.4	-0.9	1
7235	1960-01-29	CARIBOO LODGE	BC	1171393	-119.47	52.72	1096	-1	-0.4	-0.6	1
7236	1960-01-30	CARIBOO LODGE	BC	1171393	-119.47	52.72	1096	-2	-0.3	-1.7	1
7237	1960-02-03	CARIBOO LODGE	BC	1171393	-119.47	52.72	1096	-2	-1.6	-0.4	1
7238	1960-02-10	CARIBOO LODGE	BC	1171393	-119.47	52.72	1096	-12.3	-11.2	-1.1	1
7239	1960-02-17	CARIBOO LODGE	BC	1171393	-119.47	52.72	1096	-4.6	-3.5	-1.1	1
7240	1960-02-24	CARIBOO LODGE	BC	1171393	-119.47	52.72	1096	-8.6	-5.4	-3.2	1
7241	1960-02-25	CARIBOO LODGE	BC	1171393	-119.47	52.72	1096	-15.1	-13.3	-1.8	1

7242	1960-05-21	CARIBOO LODGE	BC	1171393	-119.47	52.72	1096	2.9	3.1	-0.2	1
7243	1960-06-01	CARIBOO LODGE	BC	1171393	-119.47	52.72	1096	4.8	5.8	-1	1
7244	1960-11-19	CARIBOO LODGE	BC	1171393	-119.47	52.72	1096	-0.9	-0.6	-0.3	1
7245	1960-11-25	CARIBOO LODGE	BC	1171393	-119.47	52.72	1096	-11.4	-10	-1.4	1
7246	1960-12-12	CARIBOO LODGE	BC	1171393	-119.47	52.72	1096	-3.1	-2.8	-0.3	1
7247	1960-12-28	CARIBOO LODGE	BC	1171393	-119.47	52.72	1096	-6.4	-6.1	-0.3	1
7248	1961-01-14	CARIBOO LODGE	BC	1171393	-119.47	52.72	1096	0.8	1.7	-0.9	1
7249	1961-02-04	CARIBOO LODGE	BC	1171393	-119.47	52.72	1096	-0.9	-0.6	-0.3	1
7250	1961-10-07	CARIBOO LODGE	BC	1171393	-119.47	52.72	1096	4.1	4.4	-0.3	1
7251	1961-10-08	CARIBOO LODGE	BC	1171393	-119.47	52.72	1096	1.3	1.7	-0.4	1
7252	1961-10-09	CARIBOO LODGE	BC	1171393	-119.47	52.72	1096	-1.4	-0.6	-0.8	1
7253	1961-11-01	CARIBOO LODGE	BC	1171393	-119.47	52.72	1096	-5.9	-5.6	-0.3	1
7254	1961-11-03	CARIBOO LODGE	BC	1171393	-119.47	52.72	1096	-7.6	-6.7	-0.9	1
7255	1961-11-10	CARIBOO LODGE	BC	1171393	-119.47	52.72	1096	-0.3	0	-0.3	1
7256	1961-11-19	CARIBOO LODGE	BC	1171393	-119.47	52.72	1096	-4.8	-3.9	-0.9	1
7257	1961-11-28	CARIBOO LODGE	BC	1171393	-119.47	52.72	1096	-13.7	-12.2	-1.5	1
7258	1961-12-01	CARIBOO LODGE	BC	1171393	-119.47	52.72	1096	-19.8	-18.3	-1.5	1
7259	1962-01-02	CARIBOO LODGE	BC	1171393	-119.47	52.72	1096	-0.9	-0.6	-0.3	1
7260	1962-01-03	CARIBOO LODGE	BC	1171393	-119.47	52.72	1096	-2	-1.1	-0.9	1
7261	1962-01-05	CARIBOO LODGE	BC	1171393	-119.47	52.72	1096	-1.4	-1.1	-0.3	1
7262	1962-01-07	CARIBOO LODGE	BC	1171393	-119.47	52.72	1096	-7	-5.6	-1.4	1
7263	1962-02-02	CARIBOO LODGE	BC	1171393	-119.47	52.72	1096	1.3	2.2	-0.9	1
7264	1962-12-05	CARIBOO LODGE	BC	1171393	-119.47	52.72	1096	-2	-1.1	-0.9	1
7265	1962-12-06	CARIBOO LODGE	BC	1171393	-119.47	52.72	1096	-2.6	-1.1	-1.5	1
7266	1962-12-07	CARIBOO LODGE	BC	1171393	-119.47	52.72	1096	-3.1	-1.7	-1.4	1
7267	1962-12-15	CARIBOO LODGE	BC	1171393	-119.47	52.72	1096	0.2	0.6	-0.4	1
7268	1962-12-21	CARIBOO LODGE	BC	1171393	-119.47	52.72	1096	-2.6	-1.7	-0.9	1
7269	1962-12-23	CARIBOO LODGE	BC	1171393	-119.47	52.72	1096	-8.7	-7.8	-0.9	1
7270	1963-01-01	CARIBOO LODGE	BC	1171393	-119.47	52.72	1096	-0.3	0	-0.3	1
7271	1963-01-02	CARIBOO LODGE	BC	1171393	-119.47	52.72	1096	-1.4	-1.1	-0.3	1
7272	1963-10-17	CARIBOO LODGE	BC	1171393	-119.47	52.72	1096	6.3	7.2	-0.9	1
7273	1963-10-28	CARIBOO LODGE	BC	1171393	-119.47	52.72	1096	-1.4	-0.6	-0.8	1
7274	1963-11-17	CARIBOO LODGE	BC	1171393	-119.47	52.72	1096	-3.1	-2.2	-0.9	1
7275	1963-11-18	CARIBOO LODGE	BC	1171393	-119.47	52.72	1096	-13.1	-12.2	-0.9	1

7276	1963-11-24	CARIBOO LODGE	BC	1171393	-119.47	52.72	1096	-2	-1.7	-0.3	1
7277	1963-11-25	CARIBOO LODGE	BC	1171393	-119.47	52.72	1096	-1.4	-1.1	-0.3	1
7278	1963-12-04	CARIBOO LODGE	BC	1171393	-119.47	52.72	1096	-4.2	-3.9	-0.3	1
7279	1963-12-05	CARIBOO LODGE	BC	1171393	-119.47	52.72	1096	-3.1	-2.8	-0.3	1
7280	1963-12-15	CARIBOO LODGE	BC	1171393	-119.47	52.72	1096	-11.4	-10.6	-0.8	1
7281	1963-12-31	CARIBOO LODGE	BC	1171393	-119.47	52.72	1096	-0.9	-0.6	-0.3	1
7282	1964-01-30	CARIBOO LODGE	BC	1171393	-119.47	52.72	1096	-2.6	-2.2	-0.4	1
7283	1964-02-04	CARIBOO LODGE	BC	1171393	-119.47	52.72	1096	-2	-0.6	-1.4	1
7284	1964-10-24	CARIBOO LODGE	BC	1171393	-119.47	52.72	1096	-0.9	0	-0.9	1
7285	1964-10-30	CARIBOO LODGE	BC	1171393	-119.47	52.72	1096	-1.4	0	-1.4	1
7286	1964-11-04	CARIBOO LODGE	BC	1171393	-119.47	52.72	1096	-0.9	0	-0.9	1
7287	1964-11-06	CARIBOO LODGE	BC	1171393	-119.47	52.72	1096	0.2	0.6	-0.4	1
7288	1964-11-19	CARIBOO LODGE	BC	1171393	-119.47	52.72	1096	-2	-1.7	-0.3	1
7289	1964-11-20	CARIBOO LODGE	BC	1171393	-119.47	52.72	1096	-2.6	-1.1	-1.5	1
7290	1964-11-23	CARIBOO LODGE	BC	1171393	-119.47	52.72	1096	-2	-1.7	-0.3	1
7291	1964-11-24	CARIBOO LODGE	BC	1171393	-119.47	52.72	1096	-7.6	-6.7	-0.9	1
7292	1964-11-26	CARIBOO LODGE	BC	1171393	-119.47	52.72	1096	-13.7	-12.8	-0.9	1
7293	1964-11-30	CARIBOO LODGE	BC	1171393	-119.47	52.72	1096	-8.1	-7.2	-0.9	1
7294	1964-12-07	CARIBOO LODGE	BC	1171393	-119.47	52.72	1096	-3.7	-3.3	-0.4	1
7295	1964-12-15	CARIBOO LODGE	BC	1171393	-119.47	52.72	1096	-30.9	-30	-0.9	1
7296	1965-01-17	CARIBOO LODGE	BC	1171393	-119.47	52.72	1096	-0.3	0	-0.3	1
7297	1965-01-18	CARIBOO LODGE	BC	1171393	-119.47	52.72	1096	-2	-1.1	-0.9	1
7298	1965-01-19	CARIBOO LODGE	BC	1171393	-119.47	52.72	1096	-2.6	-1.7	-0.9	1
7299	1965-01-21	CARIBOO LODGE	BC	1171393	-119.47	52.72	1096	-2	-1.7	-0.3	1
7300	1965-01-24	CARIBOO LODGE	BC	1171393	-119.47	52.72	1096	-12.6	-12.2	-0.4	1
7301	1965-01-31	CARIBOO LODGE	BC	1171393	-119.47	52.72	1096	-13.1	-12.2	-0.9	1
7302	1965-02-19	CARIBOO LODGE	BC	1171393	-119.47	52.72	1096	1.3	1.7	-0.4	1
7303	1965-04-01	CARIBOO LODGE	BC	1171393	-119.47	52.72	1096	-0.9	-0.6	-0.3	1
7304	1965-11-11	CARIBOO LODGE	BC	1171393	-119.47	52.72	1096	-2	-1.1	-0.9	1
7305	1965-11-14	CARIBOO LODGE	BC	1171393	-119.47	52.72	1096	-4.2	-3.9	-0.3	1
7306	1965-11-20	CARIBOO LODGE	BC	1171393	-119.47	52.72	1096	-1.4	-1.1	-0.3	1
7307	1965-11-30	CARIBOO LODGE	BC	1171393	-119.47	52.72	1096	-2	-1.7	-0.3	1
7308	1965-12-01	CARIBOO LODGE	BC	1171393	-119.47	52.72	1096	-1.4	-1.1	-0.3	1
7309	1965-12-02	CARIBOO LODGE	BC	1171393	-119.47	52.72	1096	-2	-1.7	-0.3	1

7310	1965-12-08	CARIBOO LODGE	BC	1171393	-119.47	52.72	1096	-2	-1.7	-0.3	1
7311	1965-12-09	CARIBOO LODGE	BC	1171393	-119.47	52.72	1096	-1.4	-1.1	-0.3	1
7312	1965-12-10	CARIBOO LODGE	BC	1171393	-119.47	52.72	1096	-2.6	-2.2	-0.4	1
7313	1965-12-12	CARIBOO LODGE	BC	1171393	-119.47	52.72	1096	-4.2	-3.9	-0.3	1
7314	1965-12-20	CARIBOO LODGE	BC	1171393	-119.47	52.72	1096	-2.6	-2.2	-0.4	1
7315	1965-12-30	CARIBOO LODGE	BC	1171393	-119.47	52.72	1096	-19.8	-18.3	-1.5	1
7316	1966-01-02	CARIBOO LODGE	BC	1171393	-119.47	52.72	1096	-22	-20.6	-1.4	1
7317	1966-01-18	CARIBOO LODGE	BC	1171393	-119.47	52.72	1096	-15.3	-13.3	-2	1
7318	1966-01-26	CARIBOO LODGE	BC	1171393	-119.47	52.72	1096	-15.3	-15	-0.3	1
7319	1966-02-04	CARIBOO LODGE	BC	1171393	-119.47	52.72	1096	-2	-1.1	-0.9	1
7320	1966-02-05	CARIBOO LODGE	BC	1171393	-119.47	52.72	1096	-0.9	0	-0.9	1
7321	1966-10-20	CARIBOO LODGE	BC	1171393	-119.47	52.72	1096	-1.4	-0.6	-0.8	1
7322	1966-11-05	CARIBOO LODGE	BC	1171393	-119.47	52.72	1096	-0.3	0	-0.3	1
7323	1966-11-15	CARIBOO LODGE	BC	1171393	-119.47	52.72	1096	-7.6	-7.2	-0.4	1
7324	1966-11-25	CARIBOO LODGE	BC	1171393	-119.47	52.72	1096	-1.4	-1.1	-0.3	1
7325	1966-12-03	CARIBOO LODGE	BC	1171393	-119.47	52.72	1096	-4.2	-3.3	-0.9	1
7326	1966-12-05	CARIBOO LODGE	BC	1171393	-119.47	52.72	1096	-13.7	-12.2	-1.5	1
7327	1966-12-07	CARIBOO LODGE	BC	1171393	-119.47	52.72	1096	-17	-16.7	-0.3	1
7328	1966-12-15	CARIBOO LODGE	BC	1171393	-119.47	52.72	1096	-0.3	0	-0.3	1
7329	1966-12-26	CARIBOO LODGE	BC	1171393	-119.47	52.72	1096	-5.9	-5	-0.9	1
7330	1967-01-16	CARIBOO LODGE	BC	1171393	-119.47	52.72	1096	-6.4	-5.6	-0.8	1
7331	1967-01-26	CARIBOO LODGE	BC	1171393	-119.47	52.72	1096	-7.6	-6.7	-0.9	1
7332	1967-10-10	CARIBOO LODGE	BC	1171393	-119.47	52.72	1096	9.1	10	-0.9	1
7333	1967-10-27	CARIBOO LODGE	BC	1171393	-119.47	52.72	1096	-3.1	-2.8	-0.3	1
7334	1967-10-30	CARIBOO LODGE	BC	1171393	-119.47	52.72	1096	-0.3	0	-0.3	1
7335	1967-11-19	CARIBOO LODGE	BC	1171393	-119.47	52.72	1096	-1.4	-1.1	-0.3	1
7336	1967-12-10	CARIBOO LODGE	BC	1171393	-119.47	52.72	1096	-2.6	-2.2	-0.4	1
7337	1967-12-28	CARIBOO LODGE	BC	1171393	-119.47	52.72	1096	-2	-0.6	-1.4	1
7338	1967-12-29	CARIBOO LODGE	BC	1171393	-119.47	52.72	1096	-2.6	-1.1	-1.5	1
7339	1968-03-13	CARIBOO LODGE	BC	1171393	-119.47	52.72	1096	-1.4	-0.6	-0.8	1
7340	1968-03-15	CARIBOO LODGE	BC	1171393	-119.47	52.72	1096	-1.4	-1.1	-0.3	1
7341	1968-04-10	CARIBOO LODGE	BC	1171393	-119.47	52.72	1096	-0.9	0	-0.9	1
7342	1968-06-01	CARIBOO LODGE	BC	1171393	-119.47	52.72	1096	6.9	7.2	-0.3	1
7343	1968-11-15	CARIBOO LODGE	BC	1171393	-119.47	52.72	1096	-4.8	-4.4	-0.4	1

7344	1968-12-10	CARIBOO LODGE	BC	1171393	-119.47	52.72	1096	-3.1	-2.2	-0.9	1
7345	1968-12-11	CARIBOO LODGE	BC	1171393	-119.47	52.72	1096	-15.9	-15	-0.9	1
7346	1968-12-18	CARIBOO LODGE	BC	1171393	-119.47	52.72	1096	-4.8	-3.9	-0.9	1
7347	1968-12-25	CARIBOO LODGE	BC	1171393	-119.47	52.72	1096	-14.2	-13.3	-0.9	1
7348	1969-09-20	CARIBOO LODGE	BC	1171393	-119.47	52.72	1096	6.9	7.2	-0.3	1
7349	1969-10-22	CARIBOO LODGE	BC	1171393	-119.47	52.72	1096	2.4	2.8	-0.4	1
7350	1969-11-12	CARIBOO LODGE	BC	1171393	-119.47	52.72	1096	0.2	0.6	-0.4	1
7351	1969-11-15	CARIBOO LODGE	BC	1171393	-119.47	52.72	1096	-0.3	0	-0.3	1
7352	1969-11-16	CARIBOO LODGE	BC	1171393	-119.47	52.72	1096	-5.3	-5	-0.3	1
7353	1969-11-23	CARIBOO LODGE	BC	1171393	-119.47	52.72	1096	-0.9	-0.6	-0.3	1
7354	1969-12-03	CARIBOO LODGE	BC	1171393	-119.47	52.72	1096	-1.4	-1.1	-0.3	1
7355	1969-12-04	CARIBOO LODGE	BC	1171393	-119.47	52.72	1096	-5.3	-4.4	-0.9	1
7356	1970-01-14	CARIBOO LODGE	BC	1171393	-119.47	52.72	1096	-20.9	-20	-0.9	1
7357	1970-12-17	CARIBOO LODGE	BC	1171393	-119.47	52.72	1096	-10.9	-10	-0.9	1
7358	1971-01-12	CARIBOO LODGE	BC	1171393	-119.47	52.72	1096	-26.4	-25.6	-0.8	1
7359	1971-01-19	CARIBOO LODGE	BC	1171393	-119.47	52.72	1096	-2.6	-2.2	-0.4	1
7360	1971-01-29	CARIBOO LODGE	BC	1171393	-119.47	52.72	1096	-3.1	-2.8	-0.3	1
7361	1971-01-30	CARIBOO LODGE	BC	1171393	-119.47	52.72	1096	-9.8	-9.4	-0.4	1
7362	1971-05-13	CARIBOO LODGE	BC	1171393	-119.47	52.72	1096	8.6	10	-1.4	1
7363	1971-06-08	CARIBOO LODGE	BC	1171393	-119.47	52.72	1096	6.3	7.8	-1.5	1
7364	1971-10-22	CARIBOO LODGE	BC	1171393	-119.47	52.72	1096	1.9	3.3	-1.4	1
7365	1971-10-25	CARIBOO LODGE	BC	1171393	-119.47	52.72	1096	1.9	2.2	-0.3	1
7366	1971-11-11	CARIBOO LODGE	BC	1171393	-119.47	52.72	1096	-0.9	0	-0.9	1
7367	1971-12-17	CARIBOO LODGE	BC	1171393	-119.47	52.72	1096	-9.8	-9.4	-0.4	1
7368	1971-12-21	CARIBOO LODGE	BC	1171393	-119.47	52.72	1096	-10.3	-9.4	-0.9	1
7369	1972-01-02	CARIBOO LODGE	BC	1171393	-119.47	52.72	1096	-8.1	-7.8	-0.3	1
7370	1972-01-09	CARIBOO LODGE	BC	1171393	-119.47	52.72	1096	-7.6	-7.2	-0.4	1
7371	1972-02-16	CARIBOO LODGE	BC	1171393	-119.47	52.72	1096	-2.6	-1.7	-0.9	1
7372	1972-02-20	CARIBOO LODGE	BC	1171393	-119.47	52.72	1096	-3.1	-2.8	-0.3	1
7373	1972-02-22	CARIBOO LODGE	BC	1171393	-119.47	52.72	1096	-8.1	-7.2	-0.9	1
7374	1972-02-25	CARIBOO LODGE	BC	1171393	-119.47	52.72	1096	-12.6	-12.2	-0.4	1
7375	1972-06-11	CARIBOO LODGE	BC	1171393	-119.47	52.72	1096	8.6	10	-1.4	1
7376	1972-11-05	CARIBOO LODGE	BC	1171393	-119.47	52.72	1096	-2	-0.6	-1.4	1
7377	1972-11-10	CARIBOO LODGE	BC	1171393	-119.47	52.72	1096	1.3	2.8	-1.5	1

7378	1972-12-21	CARIBOO LODGE	BC	1171393	-119.47	52.72	1096	0.8	1.1	-0.3	1
7379	1972-12-28	CARIBOO LODGE	BC	1171393	-119.47	52.72	1096	-10.9	-9.4	-1.5	1
7380	1973-02-02	CARIBOO LODGE	BC	1171393	-119.47	52.72	1096	-2	-1.7	-0.3	1
7381	1973-02-11	CARIBOO LODGE	BC	1171393	-119.47	52.72	1096	-11.4	-10.6	-0.8	1
7382	1973-10-06	CARIBOO LODGE	BC	1171393	-119.47	52.72	1096	4.7	5	-0.3	1
7383	1973-11-09	CARIBOO LODGE	BC	1171393	-119.47	52.72	1096	-9.8	-9.4	-0.4	1
7384	1973-11-30	CARIBOO LODGE	BC	1171393	-119.47	52.72	1096	-8.7	-8.3	-0.4	1
7385	1973-12-07	CARIBOO LODGE	BC	1171393	-119.47	52.72	1096	-0.9	-0.6	-0.3	1
7386	1973-12-13	CARIBOO LODGE	BC	1171393	-119.47	52.72	1096	-0.3	0	-0.3	1
7387	1973-12-16	CARIBOO LODGE	BC	1171393	-119.47	52.72	1096	-0.3	0.6	-0.9	1
7388	1973-12-17	CARIBOO LODGE	BC	1171393	-119.47	52.72	1096	-4.2	-3.3	-0.9	1
7389	1973-12-28	CARIBOO LODGE	BC	1171393	-119.47	52.72	1096	-10.3	-10	-0.3	1
7390	1973-12-31	CARIBOO LODGE	BC	1171393	-119.47	52.72	1096	-14.2	-13.3	-0.9	1
7391	1974-02-12	CARIBOO LODGE	BC	1171393	-119.47	52.72	1096	-3.1	-2.8	-0.3	1
7392	1974-03-02	CARIBOO LODGE	BC	1171393	-119.47	52.72	1096	-2.6	-2.2	-0.4	1
7393	1974-11-06	CARIBOO LODGE	BC	1171393	-119.47	52.72	1096	2.4	3.3	-0.9	1
7394	1974-11-12	CARIBOO LODGE	BC	1171393	-119.47	52.72	1096	-1.4	-1.1	-0.3	1
7395	1974-11-20	CARIBOO LODGE	BC	1171393	-119.47	52.72	1096	-2.6	-1.7	-0.9	1
7396	1974-11-21	CARIBOO LODGE	BC	1171393	-119.47	52.72	1096	-5.9	-5	-0.9	1
7397	1974-11-25	CARIBOO LODGE	BC	1171393	-119.47	52.72	1096	-2.6	-1.1	-1.5	1
7398	1974-12-10	CARIBOO LODGE	BC	1171393	-119.47	52.72	1096	0.2	0.6	-0.4	1
7399	1974-12-11	CARIBOO LODGE	BC	1171393	-119.47	52.72	1096	-1.4	-1.1	-0.3	1
7400	1974-12-12	CARIBOO LODGE	BC	1171393	-119.47	52.72	1096	-4.8	-2.8	-2	1
7401	1974-12-17	CARIBOO LODGE	BC	1171393	-119.47	52.72	1096	-4.2	-3.9	-0.3	1
7402	1974-12-26	CARIBOO LODGE	BC	1171393	-119.47	52.72	1096	-7	-6.7	-0.3	1
7403	1975-01-08	CARIBOO LODGE	BC	1171393	-119.47	52.72	1096	-10.3	-10	-0.3	1
7404	1975-01-09	CARIBOO LODGE	BC	1171393	-119.47	52.72	1096	-24.2	-23.9	-0.3	1
7405	1975-02-20	CARIBOO LODGE	BC	1171393	-119.47	52.72	1096	-4.2	-2.8	-1.4	1
7406	1975-03-16	CARIBOO LODGE	BC	1171393	-119.47	52.72	1096	-0.3	0.6	-0.9	1
7407	1975-11-08	CARIBOO LODGE	BC	1171393	-119.47	52.72	1096	-4.2	-3.9	-0.3	1
7408	1975-11-28	CARIBOO LODGE	BC	1171393	-119.47	52.72	1096	-20.3	-19.4	-0.9	1
7409	1975-12-09	CARIBOO LODGE	BC	1171393	-119.47	52.72	1096	-5.9	-4.4	-1.5	1
7410	1975-12-19	CARIBOO LODGE	BC	1171393	-119.47	52.72	1096	-4.2	-3.9	-0.3	1
7411	1976-01-10	CARIBOO LODGE	BC	1171393	-119.47	52.72	1096	-7.6	-7.2	-0.4	1

7412	1976-01-12	CARIBOO LODGE	BC	1171393	-119.47	52.72	1096	-8.1	-7.2	-0.9	1
7413	1976-02-08	CARIBOO LODGE	BC	1171393	-119.47	52.72	1096	-4.2	-3.3	-0.9	1
7414	1976-02-09	CARIBOO LODGE	BC	1171393	-119.47	52.72	1096	-7	-6.7	-0.3	1
7415	1976-11-24	CARIBOO LODGE	BC	1171393	-119.47	52.72	1096	-2.6	-1.7	-0.9	1
7416	1976-12-11	CARIBOO LODGE	BC	1171393	-119.47	52.72	1096	-2.6	-2.2	-0.4	1
7417	1976-12-17	CARIBOO LODGE	BC	1171393	-119.47	52.72	1096	3.6	3.9	-0.3	1
7418	1976-12-18	CARIBOO LODGE	BC	1171393	-119.47	52.72	1096	-4.2	-2.8	-1.4	1
7419	1976-12-27	CARIBOO LODGE	BC	1171393	-119.47	52.72	1096	-5.9	-5	-0.9	1
7420	1992-01-05	CARIBOO LODGE	BC	1171393	-119.47	52.72	1096	-11.5	-8	-3.5	1
7421	1992-01-11	CARIBOO LODGE	BC	1171393	-119.47	52.72	1096	-3.5	-2	-1.5	1
7422	2009-12-06	CARWAY	ALTA	3031402	-113.37	49	1354	-6	-2	-4	1
7423	1883-10-06	MINNEDOSA	MAN	5042004	-99.83	50.27	412	4.8	5	-0.2	1
7424	1897-03-30	MINNEDOSA	MAN	5042004	-99.83	50.27	412	3.7	3.8	-0.1	1
7425	1899-10-13	MINNEDOSA	MAN	5042004	-99.83	50.27	412	2.2	2.5	-0.3	1
7426	1902-03-23	MINNEDOSA	MAN	5042004	-99.83	50.27	412	3.7	3.8	-0.1	1
7427	1902-03-27	MINNEDOSA	MAN	5042004	-99.83	50.27	412	3.2	3.8	-0.6	1
7428	1914-12-05	MINNEDOSA	MAN	5042004	-99.83	50.27	412	-6.6	-6.2	-0.4	1
7429	1922-11-10	MINNEDOSA	MAN	5042004	-99.83	50.27	412	1.2	1.7	-0.5	1
7430	1924-10-03	MINNEDOSA	MAN	5042004	-99.83	50.27	412	5.5	6.4	-0.9	1
7431	1925-09-29	MINNEDOSA	MAN	5042004	-99.83	50.27	412	2.7	3.2	-0.5	1
7432	1926-11-17	MINNEDOSA	MAN	5042004	-99.83	50.27	412	-8.6	-8.4	-0.2	1
7433	1926-11-18	MINNEDOSA	MAN	5042004	-99.83	50.27	412	-9.1	-9	-0.1	1
7434	1930-10-11	MINNEDOSA	MAN	5042004	-99.83	50.27	412	4.8	5.4	-0.6	1
7435	1932-04-23	MINNEDOSA	MAN	5042004	-99.83	50.27	412	1.7	2.5	-0.8	1
7436	1935-04-23	MINNEDOSA	MAN	5042004	-99.83	50.27	412	6.7	6.9	-0.2	1
7437	1947-03-27	MINNEDOSA	MAN	5042004	-99.83	50.27	412	-0.3	0.4	-0.7	1
7438	1949-03-23	MINNEDOSA	MAN	5042004	-99.83	50.27	412	-4.3	-3.3	-1	1
7439	1950-01-12	MINNEDOSA	MAN	5042004	-99.83	50.27	412	-22.4	-21.1	-1.3	1
7440	1950-01-21	MINNEDOSA	MAN	5042004	-99.83	50.27	412	-21.3	-19.1	-2.2	1
7441	1953-01-10	MINNEDOSA	MAN	5042004	-99.83	50.27	412	-9.4	-8.8	-0.6	1
7442	1953-01-12	MINNEDOSA	MAN	5042004	-99.83	50.27	412	-16.7	-16.6	-0.1	1
7443	1953-01-19	MINNEDOSA	MAN	5042004	-99.83	50.27	412	-21.8	-21.7	-0.1	1
7444	1953-11-08	MINNEDOSA	MAN	5042004	-99.83	50.27	412	-0.2	1	-1.2	1
7445	1957-10-05	MINNEDOSA	MAN	5042004	-99.83	50.27	412	7.8	7.9	-0.1	1

7446	1957-11-16	MINNEDOSA	MAN	5042004	-99.83	50.27	412	-4.3	-2.1	-2.2	1
7447	1957-12-25	MINNEDOSA	MAN	5042004	-99.83	50.27	412	-10	-8.8	-1.2	1
7448	1957-12-27	MINNEDOSA	MAN	5042004	-99.83	50.27	412	-25.2	-20.1	-5.1	1
7449	1958-01-01	MINNEDOSA	MAN	5042004	-99.83	50.27	412	-17.3	-16.2	-1.1	1
7450	1958-01-23	MINNEDOSA	MAN	5042004	-99.83	50.27	412	-10.5	-7.1	-3.4	1
7451	1958-01-26	MINNEDOSA	MAN	5042004	-99.83	50.27	412	-7.7	-7.1	-0.6	1
7452	1959-01-02	MINNEDOSA	MAN	5042004	-99.83	50.27	412	-26.3	-25.9	-0.4	1
7453	1959-01-14	MINNEDOSA	MAN	5042004	-99.83	50.27	412	-24.6	-17.7	-6.9	1
7454	1959-01-15	MINNEDOSA	MAN	5042004	-99.83	50.27	412	-22.9	-22.7	-0.2	1
7455	1959-01-18	MINNEDOSA	MAN	5042004	-99.83	50.27	412	-21.8	-20.1	-1.7	1
7456	1959-01-21	MINNEDOSA	MAN	5042004	-99.83	50.27	412	-25.7	-24.3	-1.4	1
7457	1961-11-02	MINNEDOSA	MAN	5042004	-99.83	50.27	412	-6.1	-6	-0.1	1
7458	1962-01-08	MINNEDOSA	MAN	5042004	-99.83	50.27	412	-26.8	-24.8	-2	1
7459	1962-03-07	MINNEDOSA	MAN	5042004	-99.83	50.27	412	-8.8	-6.6	-2.2	1
7460	1962-03-23	MINNEDOSA	MAN	5042004	-99.83	50.27	412	-2	0.4	-2.4	1
7461	1964-11-16	MINNEDOSA	MAN	5042004	-99.83	50.27	412	-8.8	-5.5	-3.3	1
7462	1964-11-24	MINNEDOSA	MAN	5042004	-99.83	50.27	412	-16.2	-10.4	-5.8	1
7463	1964-11-26	MINNEDOSA	MAN	5042004	-99.83	50.27	412	-21.3	-18.7	-2.6	1
7464	1964-12-13	MINNEDOSA	MAN	5042004	-99.83	50.27	412	-20.1	-19.7	-0.4	1
7465	1964-12-14	MINNEDOSA	MAN	5042004	-99.83	50.27	412	-21.8	-20.1	-1.7	1
7466	1964-12-17	MINNEDOSA	MAN	5042004	-99.83	50.27	412	-21.8	-20.7	-1.1	1
7467	1964-12-22	MINNEDOSA	MAN	5042004	-99.83	50.27	412	-18.9	-18.7	-0.2	1
7468	1964-12-23	MINNEDOSA	MAN	5042004	-99.83	50.27	412	-21.3	-20.2	-1.1	1
7469	1965-01-20	MINNEDOSA	MAN	5042004	-99.83	50.27	412	-10.5	-8.8	-1.7	1
7470	1965-01-24	MINNEDOSA	MAN	5042004	-99.83	50.27	412	-24	-17.1	-6.9	1
7471	1965-01-25	MINNEDOSA	MAN	5042004	-99.83	50.27	412	-25.7	-18.1	-7.6	1
7472	1965-01-26	MINNEDOSA	MAN	5042004	-99.83	50.27	412	-27.4	-21.2	-6.2	1
7473	1966-03-03	MINNEDOSA	MAN	5042004	-99.83	50.27	412	-12.2	-11.9	-0.3	1
7474	1966-03-17	MINNEDOSA	MAN	5042004	-99.83	50.27	412	2.6	2.9	-0.3	1
7475	1966-03-18	MINNEDOSA	MAN	5042004	-99.83	50.27	412	-5	-3.8	-1.2	1
7476	1966-10-21	MINNEDOSA	MAN	5042004	-99.83	50.27	412	2.6	3.5	-0.9	1
7477	1966-11-06	MINNEDOSA	MAN	5042004	-99.83	50.27	412	-7.7	-7.1	-0.6	1
7478	1966-11-17	MINNEDOSA	MAN	5042004	-99.83	50.27	412	-11.1	-10.4	-0.7	1
7479	1966-12-06	MINNEDOSA	MAN	5042004	-99.83	50.27	412	-12.2	-11.9	-0.3	1

7480	1966-12-20	MINNEDOSA	MAN	5042004	-99.83	50.27	412	-8.8	-7.1	-1.7	1
7481	1967-01-31	MINNEDOSA	MAN	5042004	-99.83	50.27	412	-17.3	-17.2	-0.1	1
7482	1967-02-04	MINNEDOSA	MAN	5042004	-99.83	50.27	412	-18.4	-18.1	-0.3	1
7483	1967-02-10	MINNEDOSA	MAN	5042004	-99.83	50.27	412	-18.9	-18.1	-0.8	1
7484	1967-03-06	MINNEDOSA	MAN	5042004	-99.83	50.27	412	-17.8	-15.6	-2.2	1
7485	1967-04-17	MINNEDOSA	MAN	5042004	-99.83	50.27	412	2	2.9	-0.9	1
7486	1967-04-20	MINNEDOSA	MAN	5042004	-99.83	50.27	412	2.6	3.5	-0.9	1
7487	1967-10-26	MINNEDOSA	MAN	5042004	-99.83	50.27	412	-2.5	-1.6	-0.9	1
7488	1967-11-21	MINNEDOSA	MAN	5042004	-99.83	50.27	412	-5.5	-4.4	-1.1	1
7489	1967-11-26	MINNEDOSA	MAN	5042004	-99.83	50.27	412	-13.3	-13.1	-0.2	1
7490	1967-12-01	MINNEDOSA	MAN	5042004	-99.83	50.27	412	-5.5	-4.9	-0.6	1
7491	1967-12-07	MINNEDOSA	MAN	5042004	-99.83	50.27	412	-1.3	-1.1	-0.2	1
7492	1967-12-08	MINNEDOSA	MAN	5042004	-99.83	50.27	412	-1.3	-1.1	-0.2	1
7493	1967-12-12	MINNEDOSA	MAN	5042004	-99.83	50.27	412	-8.3	-7.7	-0.6	1
7494	1967-12-18	MINNEDOSA	MAN	5042004	-99.83	50.27	412	-10.5	-9.8	-0.7	1
7495	1967-12-21	MINNEDOSA	MAN	5042004	-99.83	50.27	412	-20.6	-19.7	-0.9	1
7496	1968-01-25	MINNEDOSA	MAN	5042004	-99.83	50.27	412	-2	-1.1	-0.9	1
7497	1968-02-27	MINNEDOSA	MAN	5042004	-99.83	50.27	412	-8.8	-4.4	-4.4	1
7498	1968-03-10	MINNEDOSA	MAN	5042004	-99.83	50.27	412	-12.7	-11.9	-0.8	1
7499	1968-03-30	MINNEDOSA	MAN	5042004	-99.83	50.27	412	0.3	1	-0.7	1
7500	1968-11-01	MINNEDOSA	MAN	5042004	-99.83	50.27	412	2.6	3	-0.4	1
7501	1968-11-06	MINNEDOSA	MAN	5042004	-99.83	50.27	412	-5	-4.4	-0.6	1
7502	1968-11-17	MINNEDOSA	MAN	5042004	-99.83	50.27	412	-2.5	-2.1	-0.4	1
7503	1968-12-12	MINNEDOSA	MAN	5042004	-99.83	50.27	412	-10	-9.4	-0.6	1
7504	1968-12-23	MINNEDOSA	MAN	5042004	-99.83	50.27	412	-19.5	-19.2	-0.3	1
7505	1969-01-16	MINNEDOSA	MAN	5042004	-99.83	50.27	412	-11.6	-9.8	-1.8	1
7506	1969-01-22	MINNEDOSA	MAN	5042004	-99.83	50.27	412	-22.9	-21.2	-1.7	1
7507	1969-02-24	MINNEDOSA	MAN	5042004	-99.83	50.27	412	-3.7	-2.1	-1.6	1
7508	1969-03-27	MINNEDOSA	MAN	5042004	-99.83	50.27	412	-8.3	-6.6	-1.7	1
7509	1969-05-15	MINNEDOSA	MAN	5042004	-99.83	50.27	412	6	6.7	-0.7	1
7510	1969-10-21	MINNEDOSA	MAN	5042004	-99.83	50.27	412	-1.3	-1.1	-0.2	1
7511	1969-11-13	MINNEDOSA	MAN	5042004	-99.83	50.27	412	-10	-9.8	-0.2	1
7512	1969-12-07	MINNEDOSA	MAN	5042004	-99.83	50.27	412	-5	-4.9	-0.1	1
7513	1969-12-11	MINNEDOSA	MAN	5042004	-99.83	50.27	412	-6.6	-6	-0.6	1

7514	1970-04-19	MINNEDOSA	MAN	5042004	-99.83	50.27	412	0.3	1	-0.7	1
7515	1970-09-21	MINNEDOSA	MAN	5042004	-99.83	50.27	412	9.6	10.4	-0.8	1
7516	1970-10-06	MINNEDOSA	MAN	5042004	-99.83	50.27	412	4.8	5.7	-0.9	1
7517	1970-11-18	MINNEDOSA	MAN	5042004	-99.83	50.27	412	-0.8	-0.6	-0.2	1
7518	1970-12-17	MINNEDOSA	MAN	5042004	-99.83	50.27	412	-15.1	-14.6	-0.5	1
7519	1971-01-29	MINNEDOSA	MAN	5042004	-99.83	50.27	412	-22.4	-22.3	-0.1	1
7520	1971-02-11	MINNEDOSA	MAN	5042004	-99.83	50.27	412	-15.1	-14.1	-1	1
7521	1971-02-17	MINNEDOSA	MAN	5042004	-99.83	50.27	412	-2	-0.6	-1.4	1
7522	1971-03-31	MINNEDOSA	MAN	5042004	-99.83	50.27	412	-0.2	0.4	-0.6	1
7523	1971-05-17	MINNEDOSA	MAN	5042004	-99.83	50.27	412	8.3	8.9	-0.6	1
7524	1971-10-27	MINNEDOSA	MAN	5042004	-99.83	50.27	412	2	3.5	-1.5	1
7525	1971-11-05	MINNEDOSA	MAN	5042004	-99.83	50.27	412	-4.4	-3.8	-0.6	1
7526	1971-11-16	MINNEDOSA	MAN	5042004	-99.83	50.27	412	0.9	1	-0.1	1
7527	1971-11-18	MINNEDOSA	MAN	5042004	-99.83	50.27	412	-2	-1.1	-0.9	1
7528	1971-11-20	MINNEDOSA	MAN	5042004	-99.83	50.27	412	-4.4	-2.7	-1.7	1
7529	1971-11-23	MINNEDOSA	MAN	5042004	-99.83	50.27	412	-3.1	-2.7	-0.4	1
7530	1971-12-16	MINNEDOSA	MAN	5042004	-99.83	50.27	412	-21.8	-20.7	-1.1	1
7531	1972-01-02	MINNEDOSA	MAN	5042004	-99.83	50.27	412	-13.9	-13.1	-0.8	1
7532	1972-01-13	MINNEDOSA	MAN	5042004	-99.83	50.27	412	-32.4	-29.2	-3.2	1
7533	1972-10-16	MINNEDOSA	MAN	5042004	-99.83	50.27	412	0.3	1.5	-1.2	1
7534	1972-10-26	MINNEDOSA	MAN	5042004	-99.83	50.27	412	4.2	4.7	-0.5	1
7535	1972-10-27	MINNEDOSA	MAN	5042004	-99.83	50.27	412	-0.2	-0.1	-0.1	1
7536	1972-11-06	MINNEDOSA	MAN	5042004	-99.83	50.27	412	-5	-4.4	-0.6	1
7537	1972-11-12	MINNEDOSA	MAN	5042004	-99.83	50.27	412	-6.1	-5.5	-0.6	1
7538	1972-11-13	MINNEDOSA	MAN	5042004	-99.83	50.27	412	-8.3	-7.1	-1.2	1
7539	1972-11-17	MINNEDOSA	MAN	5042004	-99.83	50.27	412	-7.2	-6.6	-0.6	1
7540	1972-12-22	MINNEDOSA	MAN	5042004	-99.83	50.27	412	-10	-9.4	-0.6	1
7541	1973-01-03	MINNEDOSA	MAN	5042004	-99.83	50.27	412	-18.4	-17.2	-1.2	1
7542	1973-01-04	MINNEDOSA	MAN	5042004	-99.83	50.27	412	-22.9	-22.3	-0.6	1
7543	1973-01-26	MINNEDOSA	MAN	5042004	-99.83	50.27	412	-5.5	-4.9	-0.6	1
7544	1973-04-21	MINNEDOSA	MAN	5042004	-99.83	50.27	412	2	3	-1	1
7545	1973-05-05	MINNEDOSA	MAN	5042004	-99.83	50.27	412	6	6.7	-0.7	1
7546	1973-10-25	MINNEDOSA	MAN	5042004	-99.83	50.27	412	5.4	5.7	-0.3	1
7547	1973-11-02	MINNEDOSA	MAN	5042004	-99.83	50.27	412	-3.1	-2.7	-0.4	1

7548	1973-11-14	MINNEDOSA	MAN	5042004	-99.83	50.27	412	-6.1	-6	-0.1	1
7549	1973-11-18	MINNEDOSA	MAN	5042004	-99.83	50.27	412	-8.8	-8.3	-0.5	1
7550	1973-11-27	MINNEDOSA	MAN	5042004	-99.83	50.27	412	-10	-9.4	-0.6	1
7551	1973-12-03	MINNEDOSA	MAN	5042004	-99.83	50.27	412	-12.2	-11.5	-0.7	1
7552	1973-12-12	MINNEDOSA	MAN	5042004	-99.83	50.27	412	-18.9	-17.1	-1.8	1
7553	1974-01-14	MINNEDOSA	MAN	5042004	-99.83	50.27	412	-22.9	-22.3	-0.6	1
7554	1974-02-12	MINNEDOSA	MAN	5042004	-99.83	50.27	412	-17.8	-16.6	-1.2	1
7555	1974-03-03	MINNEDOSA	MAN	5042004	-99.83	50.27	412	-11.6	-9.8	-1.8	1
7556	1974-03-06	MINNEDOSA	MAN	5042004	-99.83	50.27	412	-11.1	-9.8	-1.3	1
7557	1974-03-14	MINNEDOSA	MAN	5042004	-99.83	50.27	412	-3.7	-2.1	-1.6	1
7558	1974-03-15	MINNEDOSA	MAN	5042004	-99.83	50.27	412	-13.3	-12.5	-0.8	1
7559	1974-03-22	MINNEDOSA	MAN	5042004	-99.83	50.27	412	-24.6	-23.3	-1.3	1
7560	1974-04-27	MINNEDOSA	MAN	5042004	-99.83	50.27	412	5.4	5.7	-0.3	1
7561	1974-05-11	MINNEDOSA	MAN	5042004	-99.83	50.27	412	5.4	6.3	-0.9	1
7562	1974-09-11	MINNEDOSA	MAN	5042004	-99.83	50.27	412	8.4	8.9	-0.5	1
7563	1974-09-29	MINNEDOSA	MAN	5042004	-99.83	50.27	412	3.1	4.2	-1.1	1
7564	1974-11-12	MINNEDOSA	MAN	5042004	-99.83	50.27	412	-2.5	-1.6	-0.9	1
7565	1975-01-10	MINNEDOSA	MAN	5042004	-99.83	50.27	412	-13.9	-13.1	-0.8	1
7566	1975-01-24	MINNEDOSA	MAN	5042004	-99.83	50.27	412	-5	-4.9	-0.1	1
7567	1975-03-28	MINNEDOSA	MAN	5042004	-99.83	50.27	412	-6.6	-6	-0.6	1
7568	1975-04-26	MINNEDOSA	MAN	5042004	-99.83	50.27	412	4.8	5.7	-0.9	1
7569	1975-10-09	MINNEDOSA	MAN	5042004	-99.83	50.27	412	3.7	4.7	-1	1
7570	1975-10-14	MINNEDOSA	MAN	5042004	-99.83	50.27	412	2	2.9	-0.9	1
7571	1975-11-11	MINNEDOSA	MAN	5042004	-99.83	50.27	412	-2	-1.1	-0.9	1
7572	1975-12-05	MINNEDOSA	MAN	5042004	-99.83	50.27	412	-17.3	-15.1	-2.2	1
7573	1976-01-01	MINNEDOSA	MAN	5042004	-99.83	50.27	412	-13.9	-13.5	-0.4	1
7574	1976-01-25	MINNEDOSA	MAN	5042004	-99.83	50.27	412	-17.3	-16.2	-1.1	1
7575	1976-02-03	MINNEDOSA	MAN	5042004	-99.83	50.27	412	-18.4	-17.1	-1.3	1
7576	1976-02-10	MINNEDOSA	MAN	5042004	-99.83	50.27	412	-14.5	-12.5	-2	1
7577	1976-03-20	MINNEDOSA	MAN	5042004	-99.83	50.27	412	-10	-8.3	-1.7	1
7578	1976-04-17	MINNEDOSA	MAN	5042004	-99.83	50.27	412	2.6	2.9	-0.3	1
7579	1976-12-19	MINNEDOSA	MAN	5042004	-99.83	50.27	412	-13.9	-13.5	-0.4	1
7580	1976-12-27	MINNEDOSA	MAN	5042004	-99.83	50.27	412	-19.5	-19.1	-0.4	1
7581	1977-01-27	MINNEDOSA	MAN	5042004	-99.83	50.27	412	-29	-26.4	-2.6	1

7582	1977-02-22	MINNEDOSA	MAN	5042004	-99.83	50.27	412	-7.2	-6.6	-0.6	1
7583	1977-11-08	MINNEDOSA	MAN	5042004	-99.83	50.27	412	2	2.3	-0.3	1
7584	1977-11-17	MINNEDOSA	MAN	5042004	-99.83	50.27	412	-0.2	-0.1	-0.1	1
7585	1977-11-20	MINNEDOSA	MAN	5042004	-99.83	50.27	412	-10	-8.3	-1.7	1
7586	1977-12-08	MINNEDOSA	MAN	5042004	-99.83	50.27	412	-25.7	-24.3	-1.4	1
7587	1977-12-19	MINNEDOSA	MAN	5042004	-99.83	50.27	412	-11.6	-10.4	-1.2	1
7588	1977-12-20	MINNEDOSA	MAN	5042004	-99.83	50.27	412	-15.1	-13.5	-1.6	1
7589	1977-12-24	MINNEDOSA	MAN	5042004	-99.83	50.27	412	-22.9	-21.2	-1.7	1
7590	1978-03-11	MINNEDOSA	MAN	5042004	-99.83	50.27	412	-5	-3.3	-1.7	1
7591	1978-04-10	MINNEDOSA	MAN	5042004	-99.83	50.27	412	2	2.3	-0.3	1
7592	1978-05-31	MINNEDOSA	MAN	5042004	-99.83	50.27	412	8.3	8.9	-0.6	1
7593	1978-11-18	MINNEDOSA	MAN	5042004	-99.83	50.27	412	-15.6	-13.5	-2.1	1
7594	1978-12-05	MINNEDOSA	MAN	5042004	-99.83	50.27	412	-16.2	-14.6	-1.6	1
7595	1978-12-29	MINNEDOSA	MAN	5042004	-99.83	50.27	412	-19.5	-19.1	-0.4	1
7596	1979-03-12	MINNEDOSA	MAN	5042004	-99.83	50.27	412	-6.1	-6	-0.1	1
7597	1979-03-25	MINNEDOSA	MAN	5042004	-99.83	50.27	412	-10.5	-8.8	-1.7	1
7598	1979-12-15	MINNEDOSA	MAN	5042004	-99.83	50.27	412	-22.6	-21.7	-0.9	1
7599	1980-01-06	MINNEDOSA	MAN	5042004	-99.83	50.27	412	-18.5	-18.1	-0.4	1
7600	1980-02-06	MINNEDOSA	MAN	5042004	-99.83	50.27	412	-7.4	-6.7	-0.7	1
7601	1980-03-03	MINNEDOSA	MAN	5042004	-99.83	50.27	412	-14.5	-14.4	-0.1	1
7602	1980-12-23	MINNEDOSA	MAN	5042004	-99.83	50.27	412	-19.5	-19	-0.5	1
7603	1981-01-01	MINNEDOSA	MAN	5042004	-99.83	50.27	412	-11.4	-9.6	-1.8	1
7604	1981-10-17	MINNEDOSA	MAN	5042004	-99.83	50.27	412	7	7.3	-0.3	1
7605	1981-10-20	MINNEDOSA	MAN	5042004	-99.83	50.27	412	-0.1	0.6	-0.7	1
7606	1981-11-17	MINNEDOSA	MAN	5042004	-99.83	50.27	412	-1.1	-0.4	-0.7	1
7607	1981-11-18	MINNEDOSA	MAN	5042004	-99.83	50.27	412	-3.3	-3.2	-0.1	1
7608	1981-11-19	MINNEDOSA	MAN	5042004	-99.83	50.27	412	-5.4	-5.2	-0.2	1
7609	1981-11-27	MINNEDOSA	MAN	5042004	-99.83	50.27	412	-2.2	-1.7	-0.5	1
7610	1981-12-08	MINNEDOSA	MAN	5042004	-99.83	50.27	412	-7.4	-6.7	-0.7	1
7611	1981-12-21	MINNEDOSA	MAN	5042004	-99.83	50.27	412	-4.3	-3.7	-0.6	1
7612	1981-12-22	MINNEDOSA	MAN	5042004	-99.83	50.27	412	-11.4	-10.6	-0.8	1
7613	1981-12-27	MINNEDOSA	MAN	5042004	-99.83	50.27	412	-12.9	-11.6	-1.3	1
7614	1982-01-15	MINNEDOSA	MAN	5042004	-99.83	50.27	412	-29.6	-29.4	-0.2	1
7615	1982-03-16	MINNEDOSA	MAN	5042004	-99.83	50.27	412	1.4	1.7	-0.3	1

7616	1982-04-02	MINNEDOSA	MAN	5042004	-99.83	50.27	412	-11.4	-9.6	-1.8	1
7617	1982-10-10	MINNEDOSA	MAN	5042004	-99.83	50.27	412	6	6.8	-0.8	1
7618	1982-11-20	MINNEDOSA	MAN	5042004	-99.83	50.27	412	-5.4	-4.7	-0.7	1
7619	1982-12-19	MINNEDOSA	MAN	5042004	-99.83	50.27	412	-6.4	-5.7	-0.7	1
7620	1982-12-27	MINNEDOSA	MAN	5042004	-99.83	50.27	412	-9.4	-8.7	-0.7	1
7621	1983-01-01	MINNEDOSA	MAN	5042004	-99.83	50.27	412	-6.4	-6.2	-0.2	1
7622	1983-01-22	MINNEDOSA	MAN	5042004	-99.83	50.27	412	-4.4	-3.7	-0.7	1
7623	1983-01-29	MINNEDOSA	MAN	5042004	-99.83	50.27	412	-11.4	-10.6	-0.8	1
7624	1983-02-17	MINNEDOSA	MAN	5042004	-99.83	50.27	412	-15.5	-15.3	-0.2	1
7625	1983-02-27	MINNEDOSA	MAN	5042004	-99.83	50.27	412	-5.4	-5.2	-0.2	1
7626	1983-03-05	MINNEDOSA	MAN	5042004	-99.83	50.27	412	0.9	1.1	-0.2	1
7627	1983-03-07	MINNEDOSA	MAN	5042004	-99.83	50.27	412	-11.4	-9.6	-1.8	1
7628	1983-11-28	MINNEDOSA	MAN	5042004	-99.83	50.27	412	-9.4	-8.7	-0.7	1
7629	1984-01-25	MINNEDOSA	MAN	5042004	-99.83	50.27	412	-14.5	-13.9	-0.6	1
7630	1984-10-27	MINNEDOSA	MAN	5042004	-99.83	50.27	412	-3.3	-2.7	-0.6	1
7631	1984-11-26	MINNEDOSA	MAN	5042004	-99.83	50.27	412	-1.1	-0.8	-0.3	1
7632	1984-11-27	MINNEDOSA	MAN	5042004	-99.83	50.27	412	-6.4	-6.2	-0.2	1
7633	1984-12-16	MINNEDOSA	MAN	5042004	-99.83	50.27	412	-19.5	-18.1	-1.4	1
7634	1985-01-07	MINNEDOSA	MAN	5042004	-99.83	50.27	412	-19.5	-18.1	-1.4	1
7635	1985-02-25	MINNEDOSA	MAN	5042004	-99.83	50.27	412	-10.4	-8.7	-1.7	1
7636	1985-11-17	MINNEDOSA	MAN	5042004	-99.83	50.27	412	-8.4	-7.7	-0.7	1
7637	1985-12-09	MINNEDOSA	MAN	5042004	-99.83	50.27	412	-7.4	-6.7	-0.7	1
7638	1985-12-23	MINNEDOSA	MAN	5042004	-99.83	50.27	412	-14.5	-12.5	-2	1
7639	1986-02-07	MINNEDOSA	MAN	5042004	-99.83	50.27	412	-12.4	-11.6	-0.8	1
7640	1986-05-05	MINNEDOSA	MAN	5042004	-99.83	50.27	412	7.1	7.3	-0.2	1
7641	1986-10-30	MINNEDOSA	MAN	5042004	-99.83	50.27	412	-4.3	-3.7	-0.6	1
7642	1986-11-06	MINNEDOSA	MAN	5042004	-99.83	50.27	412	0.9	1.1	-0.2	1
7643	1986-11-08	MINNEDOSA	MAN	5042004	-99.83	50.27	412	-8.4	-6.7	-1.7	1
7644	1986-12-03	MINNEDOSA	MAN	5042004	-99.83	50.27	412	-8.4	-7.7	-0.7	1
7645	1986-12-29	MINNEDOSA	MAN	5042004	-99.83	50.27	412	-4.3	-2.7	-1.6	1
7646	1987-01-14	MINNEDOSA	MAN	5042004	-99.83	50.27	412	-13.4	-11.6	-1.8	1
7647	1987-03-07	MINNEDOSA	MAN	5042004	-99.83	50.27	412	-2.2	-1.7	-0.5	1
7648	1987-04-10	MINNEDOSA	MAN	5042004	-99.83	50.27	412	-0.6	0.1	-0.7	1
7649	1987-11-02	MINNEDOSA	MAN	5042004	-99.83	50.27	412	6	7.3	-1.3	1

7650	1987-12-11	MINNEDOSA	MAN	5042004	-99.83	50.27	412	-3.8	-2.2	-1.6	1
7651	1987-12-12	MINNEDOSA	MAN	5042004	-99.83	50.27	412	-3.8	-3.7	-0.1	1
7652	1987-12-20	MINNEDOSA	MAN	5042004	-99.83	50.27	412	-6.9	-6.2	-0.7	1
7653	1988-01-03	MINNEDOSA	MAN	5042004	-99.83	50.27	412	-23.6	-21.3	-2.3	1
7654	1988-01-30	MINNEDOSA	MAN	5042004	-99.83	50.27	412	-17.5	-16.2	-1.3	1
7655	1988-01-31	MINNEDOSA	MAN	5042004	-99.83	50.27	412	-27.1	-26.5	-0.6	1
7656	1988-03-10	MINNEDOSA	MAN	5042004	-99.83	50.27	412	1.4	2.3	-0.9	1
7657	1988-03-25	MINNEDOSA	MAN	5042004	-99.83	50.27	412	-6.4	-4.7	-1.7	1
7658	1988-11-10	MINNEDOSA	MAN	5042004	-99.83	50.27	412	-3.3	-1.7	-1.6	1
7659	1988-11-17	MINNEDOSA	MAN	5042004	-99.83	50.27	412	-9.4	-8.7	-0.7	1
7660	1988-11-25	MINNEDOSA	MAN	5042004	-99.83	50.27	412	-1.6	-0.8	-0.8	1
7661	1988-12-14	MINNEDOSA	MAN	5042004	-99.83	50.27	412	-15.5	-13.9	-1.6	1
7662	1988-12-19	MINNEDOSA	MAN	5042004	-99.83	50.27	412	-4.4	-4.2	-0.2	1
7663	1989-01-06	MINNEDOSA	MAN	5042004	-99.83	50.27	412	-15.5	-14.4	-1.1	1
7664	1989-01-31	MINNEDOSA	MAN	5042004	-99.83	50.27	412	-22.1	-19.9	-2.2	1
7665	1989-02-07	MINNEDOSA	MAN	5042004	-99.83	50.27	412	-13.4	-11.6	-1.8	1
7666	1989-04-16	MINNEDOSA	MAN	5042004	-99.83	50.27	412	-2.2	-1.7	-0.5	1
7667	1989-10-01	MINNEDOSA	MAN	5042004	-99.83	50.27	412	3.9	4.5	-0.6	1
7668	1989-12-05	MINNEDOSA	MAN	5042004	-99.83	50.27	412	-5.4	-3.7	-1.7	1
7669	1989-12-28	MINNEDOSA	MAN	5042004	-99.83	50.27	412	-11.4	-10.6	-0.8	1
7670	1990-01-11	MINNEDOSA	MAN	5042004	-99.83	50.27	412	-6.4	-4.7	-1.7	1
7671	1990-02-12	MINNEDOSA	MAN	5042004	-99.83	50.27	412	-11.9	-10.6	-1.3	1
7672	1990-03-13	MINNEDOSA	MAN	5042004	-99.83	50.27	412	1.4	2.3	-0.9	1
7673	1990-03-14	MINNEDOSA	MAN	5042004	-99.83	50.27	412	-1.1	-0.8	-0.3	1
7674	1990-04-04	MINNEDOSA	MAN	5042004	-99.83	50.27	412	-1.1	-0.8	-0.3	1
7675	1990-04-25	MINNEDOSA	MAN	5042004	-99.83	50.27	412	6	6.3	-0.3	1
7676	1990-12-18	MINNEDOSA	MAN	5042004	-99.83	50.27	412	-23.6	-21.7	-1.9	1
7677	1990-12-27	MINNEDOSA	MAN	5042004	-99.83	50.27	412	-25.6	-23.6	-2	1
7678	1990-12-28	MINNEDOSA	MAN	5042004	-99.83	50.27	412	-31.6	-30.9	-0.7	1
7679	1991-01-05	MINNEDOSA	MAN	5042004	-99.83	50.27	412	-19.5	-18.5	-1	1
7680	1991-10-23	MINNEDOSA	MAN	5042004	-99.83	50.27	412	-2.2	-1.3	-0.9	1
7681	1991-10-28	MINNEDOSA	MAN	5042004	-99.83	50.27	412	-4.3	-2.7	-1.6	1
7682	1991-10-29	MINNEDOSA	MAN	5042004	-99.83	50.27	412	-9.4	-8.7	-0.7	1
7683	1991-11-09	MINNEDOSA	MAN	5042004	-99.83	50.27	412	-7.4	-5.7	-1.7	1

7684	1991-11-21	MINNEDOSA	MAN	5042004	-99.83	50.27	412	-7.4	-6.2	-1.2	1
7685	1992-01-14	MINNEDOSA	MAN	5042004	-99.83	50.27	412	-24.6	-22.6	-2	1
7686	1992-01-17	MINNEDOSA	MAN	5042004	-99.83	50.27	412	-25.6	-23.6	-2	1
7687	1992-02-07	MINNEDOSA	MAN	5042004	-99.83	50.27	412	-11.4	-10.6	-0.8	1
7688	1992-03-07	MINNEDOSA	MAN	5042004	-99.83	50.27	412	0.4	1.7	-1.3	1
7689	1992-04-22	MINNEDOSA	MAN	5042004	-99.83	50.27	412	-0.1	0.1	-0.2	1
7690	1992-11-03	MINNEDOSA	MAN	5042004	-99.83	50.27	412	-0.1	0.1	-0.2	1
7691	1992-12-01	MINNEDOSA	MAN	5042004	-99.83	50.27	412	-1.1	-0.8	-0.3	1
7692	1993-02-05	MINNEDOSA	MAN	5042004	-99.83	50.27	412	-11.4	-10.6	-0.8	1
7693	1993-03-28	MINNEDOSA	MAN	5042004	-99.83	50.27	412	0.9	1.1	-0.2	1
7694	1993-10-28	MINNEDOSA	MAN	5042004	-99.83	50.27	412	-0.6	0.6	-1.2	1
7695	1993-11-03	MINNEDOSA	MAN	5042004	-99.83	50.27	412	-1.1	0.1	-1.2	1
7696	1993-11-04	MINNEDOSA	MAN	5042004	-99.83	50.27	412	-4.9	-3.2	-1.7	1
7697	1993-12-17	MINNEDOSA	MAN	5042004	-99.83	50.27	412	-1.1	-0.8	-0.3	1
7698	1993-12-31	MINNEDOSA	MAN	5042004	-99.83	50.27	412	-10.4	-8.7	-1.7	1
7699	1994-04-01	MINNEDOSA	MAN	5042004	-99.83	50.27	412	-0.1	1.1	-1.2	1
7700	1994-10-03	MINNEDOSA	MAN	5042004	-99.83	50.27	412	7	7.3	-0.3	1
7701	1994-10-18	MINNEDOSA	MAN	5042004	-99.83	50.27	412	11.4	11.9	-0.5	1
7702	1994-11-28	MINNEDOSA	MAN	5042004	-99.83	50.27	412	-3.3	-2.7	-0.6	1
7703	1994-12-04	MINNEDOSA	MAN	5042004	-99.83	50.27	412	-18.5	-17.2	-1.3	1
7704	1995-01-13	MINNEDOSA	MAN	5042004	-99.83	50.27	412	-12.4	-11.6	-0.8	1
7705	1995-02-03	MINNEDOSA	MAN	5042004	-99.83	50.27	412	-8.4	-7.7	-0.7	1
7706	1995-03-26	MINNEDOSA	MAN	5042004	-99.83	50.27	412	0.9	2.2	-1.3	1
7707	1995-03-27	MINNEDOSA	MAN	5042004	-99.83	50.27	412	-1.6	-0.8	-0.8	1
7708	1995-04-03	MINNEDOSA	MAN	5042004	-99.83	50.27	412	-16.5	-14.4	-2.1	1
7709	1995-04-15	MINNEDOSA	MAN	5042004	-99.83	50.27	412	3.9	4.5	-0.6	1
7710	1995-10-13	MINNEDOSA	MAN	5042004	-99.83	50.27	412	4.4	4.5	-0.1	1
7711	1995-11-02	MINNEDOSA	MAN	5042004	-99.83	50.27	412	-7.4	-6.7	-0.7	1
7712	1995-11-28	MINNEDOSA	MAN	5042004	-99.83	50.27	412	-14.5	-12.5	-2	1
7713	1995-12-05	MINNEDOSA	MAN	5042004	-99.83	50.27	412	-17.5	-17.1	-0.4	1
7714	1995-12-08	MINNEDOSA	MAN	5042004	-99.83	50.27	412	-23.6	-22.6	-1	1
7715	1996-02-23	MINNEDOSA	MAN	5042004	-99.83	50.27	412	-1.1	-0.8	-0.3	1
7716	1996-03-18	MINNEDOSA	MAN	5042004	-99.83	50.27	412	-8.4	-6.7	-1.7	1
7717	1996-04-18	MINNEDOSA	MAN	5042004	-99.83	50.27	412	-1.1	2.2	-3.3	1

7718	1996-04-19	MINNEDOSA	MAN	5042004	-99.83	50.27	412	-0.1	0.1	-0.2	1
7719	1996-04-25	MINNEDOSA	MAN	5042004	-99.83	50.27	412	1.9	2.3	-0.4	1
7720	1996-11-30	MINNEDOSA	MAN	5042004	-99.83	50.27	412	-8.4	-7.7	-0.7	1
7721	1997-04-02	MINNEDOSA	MAN	5042004	-99.83	50.27	412	0.9	1.1	-0.2	1
7722	1998-01-08	MINNEDOSA	MAN	5042004	-99.83	50.27	412	-14.5	-14.4	-0.1	1
7723	1998-10-10	MINNEDOSA	MAN	5042004	-99.83	50.27	412	4.4	4.5	-0.1	1
7724	1998-10-11	MINNEDOSA	MAN	5042004	-99.83	50.27	412	3.9	4.5	-0.6	1
7725	1998-11-10	MINNEDOSA	MAN	5042004	-99.83	50.27	412	-2.2	-1.7	-0.5	1
7726	1998-12-05	MINNEDOSA	MAN	5042004	-99.83	50.27	412	-8.4	-8.2	-0.2	1
7727	1999-05-06	MINNEDOSA	MAN	5042004	-99.83	50.27	412	8.1	8.3	-0.2	1
7728	2007-03-28	MINNEDOSA	MAN	5042004	-99.83	50.27	412	0	1	-1	1
7729	2008-08-22	MINNEDOSA	MAN	5042004	-99.83	50.27	412	14	16	-2	1
7730	1978-04-16	KINGSTON	ONT	6104142	-76.6	44.22	93	0	8	-8	1
7731	1944-03-09	QUAQTAQ	QUE	7116270	-69.63	61.05	30	-18.9	-18.5	-0.4	1
7732	1945-04-23	QUAQTAQ	QUE	7116270	-69.63	61.05	30	-5.6	-4.7	-0.9	1
7733	1945-10-14	QUAQTAQ	QUE	7116270	-69.63	61.05	30	-4.4	-4.3	-0.1	1
7734	1945-12-08	QUAQTAQ	QUE	7116270	-69.63	61.05	30	-18.9	-18.5	-0.4	1
7735	1945-12-31	QUAQTAQ	QUE	7116270	-69.63	61.05	30	-19.4	-19.1	-0.3	1
7736	1946-02-07	QUAQTAQ	QUE	7116270	-69.63	61.05	30	-18.3	-18.1	-0.2	1
7737	1946-03-01	QUAQTAQ	QUE	7116270	-69.63	61.05	30	-17.8	-17.5	-0.3	1
7738	1946-03-23	QUAQTAQ	QUE	7116270	-69.63	61.05	30	-17.8	-17.5	-0.3	1
7739	1946-03-26	QUAQTAQ	QUE	7116270	-69.63	61.05	30	-19.4	-19.1	-0.3	1
7740	1946-03-31	QUAQTAQ	QUE	7116270	-69.63	61.05	30	-20	-19.8	-0.2	1
7741	1946-04-01	QUAQTAQ	QUE	7116270	-69.63	61.05	30	-15	-14.2	-0.8	1
7742	1946-04-04	QUAQTAQ	QUE	7116270	-69.63	61.05	30	-12.2	-11.9	-0.3	1
7743	1947-03-11	QUAQTAQ	QUE	7116270	-69.63	61.05	30	-17.8	-17.5	-0.3	1
7744	1948-01-09	QUAQTAQ	QUE	7116270	-69.63	61.05	30	-15	-14.3	-0.7	1
7745	1950-01-04	QUAQTAQ	QUE	7116270	-69.63	61.05	30	-17.8	-17.5	-0.3	1
7746	1982-05-25	QUAQTAQ	QUE	7116270	-69.63	61.05	30	3.8	14.1	-10.3	1
7747	1987-08-23	QUAQTAQ	QUE	7116270	-69.63	61.05	30	4	7.5	-3.5	1
7748	1988-01-07	QUAQTAQ	QUE	7116270	-69.63	61.05	30	-24	-23	-1	1
7749	1922-02-11	CAPE SCOTT	BC	1031353	-128.43	50.78	72	-1.2	-0.7	-0.5	1
7750	1922-06-26	CAPE SCOTT	BC	1031353	-128.43	50.78	72	11.8	11.9	-0.1	1
7751	1922-10-12	CAPE SCOTT	BC	1031353	-128.43	50.78	72	11	11.8	-0.8	1

7752	1922-12-04	CAPE SCOTT	BC	1031353	-128.43	50.78	72	1	1.3	-0.3	1
7753	1922-12-08	CAPE SCOTT	BC	1031353	-128.43	50.78	72	-0.1	1.2	-1.3	1
7754	1922-12-20	CAPE SCOTT	BC	1031353	-128.43	50.78	72	6.9	7.3	-0.4	1
7755	1923-12-06	CAPE SCOTT	BC	1031353	-128.43	50.78	72	3.3	4	-0.7	1
7756	1923-12-22	CAPE SCOTT	BC	1031353	-128.43	50.78	72	3.3	3.5	-0.2	1
7757	1923-12-30	CAPE SCOTT	BC	1031353	-128.43	50.78	72	-5.6	-4.1	-1.5	1
7758	1924-01-18	CAPE SCOTT	BC	1031353	-128.43	50.78	72	2.8	3	-0.2	1
7759	1924-03-28	CAPE SCOTT	BC	1031353	-128.43	50.78	72	-0.1	0.3	-0.4	1
7760	1924-04-22	CAPE SCOTT	BC	1031353	-128.43	50.78	72	3.3	3.5	-0.2	1
7761	1924-11-09	CAPE SCOTT	BC	1031353	-128.43	50.78	72	2.1	3.5	-1.4	1
7762	1924-11-10	CAPE SCOTT	BC	1031353	-128.43	50.78	72	3.3	4	-0.7	1
7763	1924-12-15	CAPE SCOTT	BC	1031353	-128.43	50.78	72	-5.6	-4.1	-1.5	1
7764	1924-12-19	CAPE SCOTT	BC	1031353	-128.43	50.78	72	-0.6	1.2	-1.8	1
7765	1924-12-26	CAPE SCOTT	BC	1031353	-128.43	50.78	72	2.1	3	-0.9	1
7766	1924-12-27	CAPE SCOTT	BC	1031353	-128.43	50.78	72	1.6	2.1	-0.5	1
7767	1924-12-28	CAPE SCOTT	BC	1031353	-128.43	50.78	72	2.8	4	-1.2	1
7768	1924-12-29	CAPE SCOTT	BC	1031353	-128.43	50.78	72	4.9	5.2	-0.3	1
7769	1924-12-31	CAPE SCOTT	BC	1031353	-128.43	50.78	72	6.4	6.6	-0.2	1
7770	1925-01-04	CAPE SCOTT	BC	1031353	-128.43	50.78	72	5.6	5.8	-0.2	1
7771	1925-01-05	CAPE SCOTT	BC	1031353	-128.43	50.78	72	4.9	5.8	-0.9	1
7772	1925-01-11	CAPE SCOTT	BC	1031353	-128.43	50.78	72	5.6	5.8	-0.2	1
7773	1925-01-12	CAPE SCOTT	BC	1031353	-128.43	50.78	72	4.2	4.4	-0.2	1
7774	1925-01-13	CAPE SCOTT	BC	1031353	-128.43	50.78	72	3.4	4	-0.6	1
7775	1925-01-16	CAPE SCOTT	BC	1031353	-128.43	50.78	72	6.4	6.6	-0.2	1
7776	1925-01-31	CAPE SCOTT	BC	1031353	-128.43	50.78	72	1	1.2	-0.2	1
7777	1925-02-06	CAPE SCOTT	BC	1031353	-128.43	50.78	72	5.7	6.1	-0.4	1
7778	1925-02-08	CAPE SCOTT	BC	1031353	-128.43	50.78	72	5.7	5.8	-0.1	1
7779	1925-11-15	CAPE SCOTT	BC	1031353	-128.43	50.78	72	9	9.1	-0.1	1
7780	1925-12-01	CAPE SCOTT	BC	1031353	-128.43	50.78	72	3.3	4	-0.7	1
7781	1926-01-18	CAPE SCOTT	BC	1031353	-128.43	50.78	72	6.5	6.6	-0.1	1
7782	1926-02-03	CAPE SCOTT	BC	1031353	-128.43	50.78	72	6.9	7.2	-0.3	1
7783	1926-02-17	CAPE SCOTT	BC	1031353	-128.43	50.78	72	6.9	7.2	-0.3	1
7784	1926-02-23	CAPE SCOTT	BC	1031353	-128.43	50.78	72	4.1	5.3	-1.2	1
7785	1926-07-22	CAPE SCOTT	BC	1031353	-128.43	50.78	72	11.1	11.2	-0.1	1

7786	1926-07-27	CAPE SCOTT	BC	1031353	-128.43	50.78	72	13.4	13.6	-0.2	1
7787	1926-12-14	CAPE SCOTT	BC	1031353	-128.43	50.78	72	-2.3	0.3	-2.6	1
7788	1926-12-24	CAPE SCOTT	BC	1031353	-128.43	50.78	72	2.1	2.4	-0.3	1
7789	1926-12-27	CAPE SCOTT	BC	1031353	-128.43	50.78	72	3.4	4.5	-1.1	1
7790	1927-01-01	CAPE SCOTT	BC	1031353	-128.43	50.78	72	6.5	6.6	-0.1	1
7791	1927-01-02	CAPE SCOTT	BC	1031353	-128.43	50.78	72	6.5	6.6	-0.1	1
7792	1927-01-03	CAPE SCOTT	BC	1031353	-128.43	50.78	72	3.4	4	-0.6	1
7793	1927-01-13	CAPE SCOTT	BC	1031353	-128.43	50.78	72	1	1.7	-0.7	1
7794	1927-01-16	CAPE SCOTT	BC	1031353	-128.43	50.78	72	4.1	4.5	-0.4	1
7795	1927-01-17	CAPE SCOTT	BC	1031353	-128.43	50.78	72	3.4	4.5	-1.1	1
7796	1927-01-18	CAPE SCOTT	BC	1031353	-128.43	50.78	72	-0.6	0.3	-0.9	1
7797	1927-01-22	CAPE SCOTT	BC	1031353	-128.43	50.78	72	0.5	1.5	-1	1
7798	1927-01-23	CAPE SCOTT	BC	1031353	-128.43	50.78	72	2.1	3	-0.9	1
7799	1927-01-25	CAPE SCOTT	BC	1031353	-128.43	50.78	72	4.9	5.9	-1	1
7800	1927-01-26	CAPE SCOTT	BC	1031353	-128.43	50.78	72	3.4	5.2	-1.8	1
7801	1927-01-28	CAPE SCOTT	BC	1031353	-128.43	50.78	72	4.9	5.2	-0.3	1
7802	1927-01-31	CAPE SCOTT	BC	1031353	-128.43	50.78	72	2.1	2.4	-0.3	1
7803	1927-02-01	CAPE SCOTT	BC	1031353	-128.43	50.78	72	2.1	3.5	-1.4	1
7804	1927-02-04	CAPE SCOTT	BC	1031353	-128.43	50.78	72	2.1	3.5	-1.4	1
7805	1927-02-08	CAPE SCOTT	BC	1031353	-128.43	50.78	72	4.9	5.9	-1	1
7806	1927-02-10	CAPE SCOTT	BC	1031353	-128.43	50.78	72	5.8	5.9	-0.1	1
7807	1927-02-14	CAPE SCOTT	BC	1031353	-128.43	50.78	72	5.8	5.9	-0.1	1
7808	1927-02-17	CAPE SCOTT	BC	1031353	-128.43	50.78	72	2.1	3.5	-1.4	1
7809	1927-02-22	CAPE SCOTT	BC	1031353	-128.43	50.78	72	5	5.9	-0.9	1
7810	1927-02-24	CAPE SCOTT	BC	1031353	-128.43	50.78	72	5.8	5.9	-0.1	1
7811	1927-06-28	CAPE SCOTT	BC	1031353	-128.43	50.78	72	11.3	11.6	-0.3	1
7812	1927-09-02	CAPE SCOTT	BC	1031353	-128.43	50.78	72	11	11.1	-0.1	1
7813	1927-10-18	CAPE SCOTT	BC	1031353	-128.43	50.78	72	6.9	7.8	-0.9	1
7814	1927-12-13	CAPE SCOTT	BC	1031353	-128.43	50.78	72	0.5	1.2	-0.7	1
7815	1927-12-14	CAPE SCOTT	BC	1031353	-128.43	50.78	72	-3.4	-3	-0.4	1
7816	1927-12-15	CAPE SCOTT	BC	1031353	-128.43	50.78	72	2.1	3	-0.9	1
7817	1927-12-28	CAPE SCOTT	BC	1031353	-128.43	50.78	72	-0.1	0.7	-0.8	1
7818	1928-01-01	CAPE SCOTT	BC	1031353	-128.43	50.78	72	-1.2	0.3	-1.5	1
7819	1928-01-06	CAPE SCOTT	BC	1031353	-128.43	50.78	72	2.1	2.4	-0.3	1

7820	1928-01-09	CAPE SCOTT	BC	1031353	-128.43	50.78	72	11.1	11.3	-0.2	1
7821	1928-01-26	CAPE SCOTT	BC	1031353	-128.43	50.78	72	3.3	4	-0.7	1
7822	1928-02-05	CAPE SCOTT	BC	1031353	-128.43	50.78	72	3.3	3.5	-0.2	1
7823	1928-02-18	CAPE SCOTT	BC	1031353	-128.43	50.78	72	3.3	4.5	-1.2	1
7824	1928-02-24	CAPE SCOTT	BC	1031353	-128.43	50.78	72	3.3	3.5	-0.2	1
7825	1928-05-15	CAPE SCOTT	BC	1031353	-128.43	50.78	72	10.4	11.3	-0.9	1
7826	1928-09-05	CAPE SCOTT	BC	1031353	-128.43	50.78	72	11	11.3	-0.3	1
7827	1928-11-03	CAPE SCOTT	BC	1031353	-128.43	50.78	72	11	11.3	-0.3	1
7828	1929-01-15	CAPE SCOTT	BC	1031353	-128.43	50.78	72	2.1	3	-0.9	1
7829	1929-01-20	CAPE SCOTT	BC	1031353	-128.43	50.78	72	1.6	3	-1.4	1
7830	1929-01-26	CAPE SCOTT	BC	1031353	-128.43	50.78	72	-2.3	-1.8	-0.5	1
7831	1929-02-09	CAPE SCOTT	BC	1031353	-128.43	50.78	72	2.1	3	-0.9	1
7832	1929-02-16	CAPE SCOTT	BC	1031353	-128.43	50.78	72	5.7	6.7	-1	1
7833	1929-03-04	CAPE SCOTT	BC	1031353	-128.43	50.78	72	2.1	3	-0.9	1
7834	1929-03-05	CAPE SCOTT	BC	1031353	-128.43	50.78	72	1	2.4	-1.4	1
7835	1929-03-27	CAPE SCOTT	BC	1031353	-128.43	50.78	72	3.3	4.1	-0.8	1
7836	1929-06-17	CAPE SCOTT	BC	1031353	-128.43	50.78	72	11.1	11.3	-0.2	1
7837	1929-10-16	CAPE SCOTT	BC	1031353	-128.43	50.78	72	11.1	11.2	-0.1	1
7838	1929-12-09	CAPE SCOTT	BC	1031353	-128.43	50.78	72	-2.3	-0.2	-2.1	1
7839	1929-12-11	CAPE SCOTT	BC	1031353	-128.43	50.78	72	1	1.3	-0.3	1
7840	1929-12-14	CAPE SCOTT	BC	1031353	-128.43	50.78	72	1.6	3	-1.4	1
7841	1929-12-15	CAPE SCOTT	BC	1031353	-128.43	50.78	72	2.1	3	-0.9	1
7842	1930-01-05	CAPE SCOTT	BC	1031353	-128.43	50.78	72	0.5	1.3	-0.8	1
7843	1930-01-17	CAPE SCOTT	BC	1031353	-128.43	50.78	72	-3.4	-3	-0.4	1
7844	1930-01-18	CAPE SCOTT	BC	1031353	-128.43	50.78	72	-2.3	-1.8	-0.5	1
7845	1930-02-01	CAPE SCOTT	BC	1031353	-128.43	50.78	72	7.8	8.1	-0.3	1
7846	1930-02-13	CAPE SCOTT	BC	1031353	-128.43	50.78	72	2.1	4	-1.9	1
7847	1930-02-15	CAPE SCOTT	BC	1031353	-128.43	50.78	72	2.2	3	-0.8	1
7848	1930-02-26	CAPE SCOTT	BC	1031353	-128.43	50.78	72	1	1.3	-0.3	1
7849	1930-03-04	CAPE SCOTT	BC	1031353	-128.43	50.78	72	1.6	3	-1.4	1
7850	1930-03-05	CAPE SCOTT	BC	1031353	-128.43	50.78	72	3.4	3.5	-0.1	1
7851	1930-07-06	CAPE SCOTT	BC	1031353	-128.43	50.78	72	13.4	13.6	-0.2	1
7852	1930-09-21	CAPE SCOTT	BC	1031353	-128.43	50.78	72	11.1	12.1	-1	1
7853	1930-11-19	CAPE SCOTT	BC	1031353	-128.43	50.78	72	3.3	4.5	-1.2	1

7854	1930-11-30	CAPE SCOTT	BC	1031353	-128.43	50.78	72	6.8	7.3	-0.5	1
7855	1930-12-20	CAPE SCOTT	BC	1031353	-128.43	50.78	72	6.4	6.7	-0.3	1
7856	1930-12-21	CAPE SCOTT	BC	1031353	-128.43	50.78	72	5.8	5.9	-0.1	1
7857	1930-12-22	CAPE SCOTT	BC	1031353	-128.43	50.78	72	6.4	6.7	-0.3	1
7858	1931-07-12	CAPE SCOTT	BC	1031353	-128.43	50.78	72	11.6	12	-0.4	1
7859	1931-10-13	CAPE SCOTT	BC	1031353	-128.43	50.78	72	11.1	11.3	-0.2	1
7860	1931-10-17	CAPE SCOTT	BC	1031353	-128.43	50.78	72	11.1	11.3	-0.2	1
7861	1932-01-15	CAPE SCOTT	BC	1031353	-128.43	50.78	72	0.5	1.4	-0.9	1
7862	1932-01-16	CAPE SCOTT	BC	1031353	-128.43	50.78	72	0.5	1.4	-0.9	1
7863	1932-01-29	CAPE SCOTT	BC	1031353	-128.43	50.78	72	0.5	1.1	-0.6	1
7864	1932-01-30	CAPE SCOTT	BC	1031353	-128.43	50.78	72	-5.1	-2.4	-2.7	1
7865	1932-02-04	CAPE SCOTT	BC	1031353	-128.43	50.78	72	1	2.4	-1.4	1
7866	1932-07-03	CAPE SCOTT	BC	1031353	-128.43	50.78	72	11	11.3	-0.3	1
7867	1932-07-11	CAPE SCOTT	BC	1031353	-128.43	50.78	72	11.6	11.7	-0.1	1
7868	1932-09-06	CAPE SCOTT	BC	1031353	-128.43	50.78	72	11.5	12	-0.5	1
7869	1932-11-07	CAPE SCOTT	BC	1031353	-128.43	50.78	72	6.5	6.6	-0.1	1
7870	1932-12-05	CAPE SCOTT	BC	1031353	-128.43	50.78	72	3.4	3.5	-0.1	1
7871	1932-12-21	CAPE SCOTT	BC	1031353	-128.43	50.78	72	3.4	4.4	-1	1
7872	1932-12-31	CAPE SCOTT	BC	1031353	-128.43	50.78	72	3.4	3.5	-0.1	1
7873	1933-01-15	CAPE SCOTT	BC	1031353	-128.43	50.78	72	3.4	3.5	-0.1	1
7874	1933-01-21	CAPE SCOTT	BC	1031353	-128.43	50.78	72	3.4	4.1	-0.7	1
7875	1933-01-29	CAPE SCOTT	BC	1031353	-128.43	50.78	72	2.1	2.4	-0.3	1
7876	1933-01-30	CAPE SCOTT	BC	1031353	-128.43	50.78	72	2.1	2.4	-0.3	1
7877	1933-02-06	CAPE SCOTT	BC	1031353	-128.43	50.78	72	-1.2	0.3	-1.5	1
7878	1933-02-07	CAPE SCOTT	BC	1031353	-128.43	50.78	72	-1.2	0.3	-1.5	1
7879	1933-02-08	CAPE SCOTT	BC	1031353	-128.43	50.78	72	-2.3	-0.7	-1.6	1
7880	1933-02-14	CAPE SCOTT	BC	1031353	-128.43	50.78	72	3.4	3.5	-0.1	1
7881	1933-02-19	CAPE SCOTT	BC	1031353	-128.43	50.78	72	5	5.8	-0.8	1
7882	1933-02-27	CAPE SCOTT	BC	1031353	-128.43	50.78	72	3.4	3.5	-0.1	1
7883	1933-03-01	CAPE SCOTT	BC	1031353	-128.43	50.78	72	3.4	4.1	-0.7	1
7884	1933-03-04	CAPE SCOTT	BC	1031353	-128.43	50.78	72	3.3	4.5	-1.2	1
7885	1933-05-24	CAPE SCOTT	BC	1031353	-128.43	50.78	72	11.2	11.3	-0.1	1
7886	1933-09-11	CAPE SCOTT	BC	1031353	-128.43	50.78	72	11.7	11.8	-0.1	1
7887	1933-09-18	CAPE SCOTT	BC	1031353	-128.43	50.78	72	11.7	12	-0.3	1

7888	1933-09-25	CAPE SCOTT	BC	1031353	-128.43	50.78	72	9.3	9.6	-0.3	1
7889	1933-09-26	CAPE SCOTT	BC	1031353	-128.43	50.78	72	11.1	11.3	-0.2	1
7890	1933-10-02	CAPE SCOTT	BC	1031353	-128.43	50.78	72	11.1	11.3	-0.2	1
7891	1933-10-10	CAPE SCOTT	BC	1031353	-128.43	50.78	72	10.4	11.2	-0.8	1
7892	1933-11-05	CAPE SCOTT	BC	1031353	-128.43	50.78	72	6.9	7.3	-0.4	1
7893	1933-11-10	CAPE SCOTT	BC	1031353	-128.43	50.78	72	9.3	9.6	-0.3	1
7894	1933-11-12	CAPE SCOTT	BC	1031353	-128.43	50.78	72	10.4	11.2	-0.8	1
7895	1933-11-30	CAPE SCOTT	BC	1031353	-128.43	50.78	72	7.8	8.1	-0.3	1
7896	1933-12-12	CAPE SCOTT	BC	1031353	-128.43	50.78	72	1.6	1.8	-0.2	1
7897	1933-12-13	CAPE SCOTT	BC	1031353	-128.43	50.78	72	2.8	3.5	-0.7	1
7898	1933-12-15	CAPE SCOTT	BC	1031353	-128.43	50.78	72	-3.4	-0.3	-3.1	1
7899	1934-09-12	CAPE SCOTT	BC	1031353	-128.43	50.78	72	11.1	11.2	-0.1	1
7900	1935-01-14	CAPE SCOTT	BC	1031353	-128.43	50.78	72	-0.1	1.1	-1.2	1
7901	1935-01-16	CAPE SCOTT	BC	1031353	-128.43	50.78	72	-3.4	-3	-0.4	1
7902	1935-01-19	CAPE SCOTT	BC	1031353	-128.43	50.78	72	-4	-3	-1	1
7903	1935-01-21	CAPE SCOTT	BC	1031353	-128.43	50.78	72	1.6	2	-0.4	1
7904	1935-01-22	CAPE SCOTT	BC	1031353	-128.43	50.78	72	0.5	1.1	-0.6	1
7905	1935-02-15	CAPE SCOTT	BC	1031353	-128.43	50.78	72	7.3	7.9	-0.6	1
7906	1935-03-10	CAPE SCOTT	BC	1031353	-128.43	50.78	72	6.5	6.6	-0.1	1
7907	1935-03-11	CAPE SCOTT	BC	1031353	-128.43	50.78	72	5	5.9	-0.9	1
7908	1935-05-22	CAPE SCOTT	BC	1031353	-128.43	50.78	72	9	9.1	-0.1	1
7909	1935-07-29	CAPE SCOTT	BC	1031353	-128.43	50.78	72	11.6	11.9	-0.3	1
7910	1935-08-30	CAPE SCOTT	BC	1031353	-128.43	50.78	72	11.6	11.9	-0.3	1
7911	1935-11-10	CAPE SCOTT	BC	1031353	-128.43	50.78	72	4.1	5.4	-1.3	1
7912	1935-12-13	CAPE SCOTT	BC	1031353	-128.43	50.78	72	6.9	7.3	-0.4	1
7913	1935-12-22	CAPE SCOTT	BC	1031353	-128.43	50.78	72	5.6	6.3	-0.7	1
7914	1935-12-23	CAPE SCOTT	BC	1031353	-128.43	50.78	72	5.6	6.3	-0.7	1
7915	1935-12-25	CAPE SCOTT	BC	1031353	-128.43	50.78	72	9.2	9.7	-0.5	1
7916	1936-01-05	CAPE SCOTT	BC	1031353	-128.43	50.78	72	4.9	5.2	-0.3	1
7917	1936-01-18	CAPE SCOTT	BC	1031353	-128.43	50.78	72	3.3	4.6	-1.3	1
7918	1936-01-19	CAPE SCOTT	BC	1031353	-128.43	50.78	72	4.2	4.6	-0.4	1
7919	1936-02-03	CAPE SCOTT	BC	1031353	-128.43	50.78	72	2.1	3	-0.9	1
7920	1936-02-06	CAPE SCOTT	BC	1031353	-128.43	50.78	72	-6.8	-4.6	-2.2	1
7921	1936-02-07	CAPE SCOTT	BC	1031353	-128.43	50.78	72	-3.4	-0.7	-2.7	1

7922	1936-02-19	CAPE SCOTT	BC	1031353	-128.43	50.78	72	1.6	1.8	-0.2	1
7923	1936-02-24	CAPE SCOTT	BC	1031353	-128.43	50.78	72	1	1.1	-0.1	1
7924	1936-02-26	CAPE SCOTT	BC	1031353	-128.43	50.78	72	4.9	5.2	-0.3	1
7925	1936-05-13	CAPE SCOTT	BC	1031353	-128.43	50.78	72	11	11.3	-0.3	1
7926	1936-05-31	CAPE SCOTT	BC	1031353	-128.43	50.78	72	10.9	11.3	-0.4	1
7927	1936-08-14	CAPE SCOTT	BC	1031353	-128.43	50.78	72	13.4	13.6	-0.2	1
7928	1936-09-17	CAPE SCOTT	BC	1031353	-128.43	50.78	72	11.6	11.9	-0.3	1
7929	1936-09-23	CAPE SCOTT	BC	1031353	-128.43	50.78	72	11.2	11.9	-0.7	1
7930	1936-10-23	CAPE SCOTT	BC	1031353	-128.43	50.78	72	11.2	11.9	-0.7	1
7931	1936-11-15	CAPE SCOTT	BC	1031353	-128.43	50.78	72	11.6	12	-0.4	1
7932	1937-01-08	CAPE SCOTT	BC	1031353	-128.43	50.78	72	1.6	1.7	-0.1	1
7933	1937-01-14	CAPE SCOTT	BC	1031353	-128.43	50.78	72	0.5	0.7	-0.2	1
7934	1937-02-06	CAPE SCOTT	BC	1031353	-128.43	50.78	72	1	1.7	-0.7	1
7935	1937-02-14	CAPE SCOTT	BC	1031353	-128.43	50.78	72	1	2.1	-1.1	1
7936	1937-06-26	CAPE SCOTT	BC	1031353	-128.43	50.78	72	11.2	11.7	-0.5	1
7937	1937-08-29	CAPE SCOTT	BC	1031353	-128.43	50.78	72	11.8	11.9	-0.1	1
7938	1937-11-08	CAPE SCOTT	BC	1031353	-128.43	50.78	72	6.8	7.3	-0.5	1
7939	1937-11-14	CAPE SCOTT	BC	1031353	-128.43	50.78	72	-0.1	0.3	-0.4	1
7940	1937-11-26	CAPE SCOTT	BC	1031353	-128.43	50.78	72	5.6	6.3	-0.7	1
7941	1937-12-07	CAPE SCOTT	BC	1031353	-128.43	50.78	72	5.6	5.9	-0.3	1
7942	1937-12-23	CAPE SCOTT	BC	1031353	-128.43	50.78	72	1.6	2.4	-0.8	1
7943	1937-12-24	CAPE SCOTT	BC	1031353	-128.43	50.78	72	-2.3	-1.3	-1	1
7944	1937-12-29	CAPE SCOTT	BC	1031353	-128.43	50.78	72	5.7	5.9	-0.2	1
7945	1938-01-02	CAPE SCOTT	BC	1031353	-128.43	50.78	72	6.8	7.3	-0.5	1
7946	1938-01-09	CAPE SCOTT	BC	1031353	-128.43	50.78	72	6.8	7.3	-0.5	1
7947	1938-01-10	CAPE SCOTT	BC	1031353	-128.43	50.78	72	4.2	4.4	-0.2	1
7948	1938-01-30	CAPE SCOTT	BC	1031353	-128.43	50.78	72	0.5	1.4	-0.9	1
7949	1938-02-05	CAPE SCOTT	BC	1031353	-128.43	50.78	72	2.1	2.4	-0.3	1
7950	1938-02-13	CAPE SCOTT	BC	1031353	-128.43	50.78	72	2.1	3.5	-1.4	1
7951	1938-06-29	CAPE SCOTT	BC	1031353	-128.43	50.78	72	11.4	11.8	-0.4	1
7952	1938-09-05	CAPE SCOTT	BC	1031353	-128.43	50.78	72	11.4	12.5	-1.1	1
7953	1938-10-03	CAPE SCOTT	BC	1031353	-128.43	50.78	72	11.3	11.9	-0.6	1
7954	1938-10-09	CAPE SCOTT	BC	1031353	-128.43	50.78	72	11.3	11.9	-0.6	1
7955	1938-11-29	CAPE SCOTT	BC	1031353	-128.43	50.78	72	9.6	10.4	-0.8	1

7956	1938-12-09	CAPE SCOTT	BC	1031353	-128.43	50.78	72	6.4	6.6	-0.2	1
7957	1938-12-23	CAPE SCOTT	BC	1031353	-128.43	50.78	72	6.9	7.3	-0.4	1
7958	1938-12-26	CAPE SCOTT	BC	1031353	-128.43	50.78	72	1.6	2.4	-0.8	1
7959	1938-12-27	CAPE SCOTT	BC	1031353	-128.43	50.78	72	3.3	3.5	-0.2	1
7960	1939-01-09	CAPE SCOTT	BC	1031353	-128.43	50.78	72	6.4	6.7	-0.3	1
7961	1939-02-07	CAPE SCOTT	BC	1031353	-128.43	50.78	72	-0.1	0.8	-0.9	1
7962	1939-02-08	CAPE SCOTT	BC	1031353	-128.43	50.78	72	-2.9	-0.7	-2.2	1
7963	1939-02-17	CAPE SCOTT	BC	1031353	-128.43	50.78	72	6.5	6.7	-0.2	1
7964	1939-03-05	CAPE SCOTT	BC	1031353	-128.43	50.78	72	3.3	3.5	-0.2	1
7965	1939-04-28	CAPE SCOTT	BC	1031353	-128.43	50.78	72	6.8	7.9	-1.1	1
7966	1939-06-18	CAPE SCOTT	BC	1031353	-128.43	50.78	72	11.1	11.2	-0.1	1
7967	1939-07-04	CAPE SCOTT	BC	1031353	-128.43	50.78	72	11.7	11.9	-0.2	1
7968	1939-09-23	CAPE SCOTT	BC	1031353	-128.43	50.78	72	11.1	11.8	-0.7	1
7969	1939-10-12	CAPE SCOTT	BC	1031353	-128.43	50.78	72	11.1	11.8	-0.7	1
7970	1939-11-29	CAPE SCOTT	BC	1031353	-128.43	50.78	72	8.9	9.1	-0.2	1
7971	1939-12-07	CAPE SCOTT	BC	1031353	-128.43	50.78	72	7.9	8.2	-0.3	1
7972	1940-01-19	CAPE SCOTT	BC	1031353	-128.43	50.78	72	4.9	5.2	-0.3	1
7973	1940-01-23	CAPE SCOTT	BC	1031353	-128.43	50.78	72	8	8.2	-0.2	1
7974	1940-02-16	CAPE SCOTT	BC	1031353	-128.43	50.78	72	5.8	5.9	-0.1	1
7975	1940-03-07	CAPE SCOTT	BC	1031353	-128.43	50.78	72	6.5	6.7	-0.2	1
7976	1940-10-19	CAPE SCOTT	BC	1031353	-128.43	50.78	72	13.9	14.1	-0.2	1
7977	1940-11-26	CAPE SCOTT	BC	1031353	-128.43	50.78	72	7.3	7.8	-0.5	1
7978	1940-12-04	CAPE SCOTT	BC	1031353	-128.43	50.78	72	7.8	8.3	-0.5	1
7979	1940-12-22	CAPE SCOTT	BC	1031353	-128.43	50.78	72	5.7	5.9	-0.2	1
7980	1941-02-11	CAPE SCOTT	BC	1031353	-128.43	50.78	72	6.5	6.6	-0.1	1
7981	1941-09-15	CAPE SCOTT	BC	1031353	-128.43	50.78	72	9.6	10.3	-0.7	1
7982	1941-10-30	CAPE SCOTT	BC	1031353	-128.43	50.78	72	8.6	8.7	-0.1	1
7983	1941-12-07	CAPE SCOTT	BC	1031353	-128.43	50.78	72	6.8	7.2	-0.4	1
7984	1942-10-07	CAPE SCOTT	BC	1031353	-128.43	50.78	72	11.5	11.8	-0.3	1
7985	1942-11-05	CAPE SCOTT	BC	1031353	-128.43	50.78	72	2.1	2.4	-0.3	1
7986	1942-11-25	CAPE SCOTT	BC	1031353	-128.43	50.78	72	2.8	3.5	-0.7	1
7987	1942-12-04	CAPE SCOTT	BC	1031353	-128.43	50.78	72	1.6	2.4	-0.8	1
7988	1943-01-16	CAPE SCOTT	BC	1031353	-128.43	50.78	72	-3.4	-3	-0.4	1
7989	1943-01-24	CAPE SCOTT	BC	1031353	-128.43	50.78	72	0.5	0.7	-0.2	1

7990	1943-02-21	CAPE SCOTT	BC	1031353	-128.43	50.78	72	5.6	5.9	-0.3	1
7991	1943-07-14	CAPE SCOTT	BC	1031353	-128.43	50.78	72	12.4	13	-0.6	1
7992	1944-01-28	CAPE SCOTT	BC	1031353	-128.43	50.78	72	5.6	6.1	-0.5	1
7993	1944-02-24	CAPE SCOTT	BC	1031353	-128.43	50.78	72	5.7	5.9	-0.2	1
7994	1944-03-15	CAPE SCOTT	BC	1031353	-128.43	50.78	72	6.5	6.7	-0.2	1
7995	1944-06-23	CAPE SCOTT	BC	1031353	-128.43	50.78	72	11.2	11.9	-0.7	1
7996	1944-07-08	CAPE SCOTT	BC	1031353	-128.43	50.78	72	11.6	11.8	-0.2	1
7997	1944-08-28	CAPE SCOTT	BC	1031353	-128.43	50.78	72	11.6	11.9	-0.3	1
7998	1944-09-29	CAPE SCOTT	BC	1031353	-128.43	50.78	72	11.1	11.3	-0.2	1
7999	1944-10-14	CAPE SCOTT	BC	1031353	-128.43	50.78	72	11.6	11.9	-0.3	1
8000	1944-11-16	CAPE SCOTT	BC	1031353	-128.43	50.78	72	7.8	8.2	-0.4	1
8001	1944-11-17	CAPE SCOTT	BC	1031353	-128.43	50.78	72	7.3	7.9	-0.6	1
8002	1953-01-11	CAPE SCOTT	BC	1031353	-128.43	50.78	72	2.4	3.3	-0.9	1
8003	1955-12-27	CAPE SCOTT	BC	1031353	-128.43	50.78	72	1.3	1.8	-0.5	1
8004	1958-12-07	CAPE SCOTT	BC	1031353	-128.43	50.78	72	1.9	2.2	-0.3	1
8005	1986-08-27	KOMAKUK BEACH	YT	2100682	-140.2	69.62	13	-4.2	-1	-3.2	1
8006	1994-09-16	KOMAKUK BEACH	YT	2100682	-140.2	69.62	13	-2.2	-1.8	-0.4	1
8007	2004-03-27	KOMAKUK BEACH	YT	2100682	-140.2	69.62	13	-31.7	-31.6	-0.1	1
8008	2004-03-28	KOMAKUK BEACH	YT	2100682	-140.2	69.62	13	-31.6	-29.7	-1.9	1
8009	2004-03-29	KOMAKUK BEACH	YT	2100682	-140.2	69.62	13	-29	-26.1	-2.9	1
8010	2010-04-26	KOMAKUK BEACH	YT	2100682	-140.2	69.62	13	-6.2	-4.4	-1.8	1
8011	1928-05-26	CAPE DORSET	NU	2400637	-76.5	64.2	48	-1.4	-1	-0.4	1
8012	1929-08-29	CAPE DORSET	NU	2400637	-76.5	64.2	48	-0.8	-0.5	-0.3	1
8013	1930-06-27	CAPE DORSET	NU	2400637	-76.5	64.2	48	-1.4	-1	-0.4	1
8014	1931-09-14	CAPE DORSET	NU	2400637	-76.5	64.2	48	-1.2	-1	-0.2	1
8015	1932-09-19	CAPE DORSET	NU	2400637	-76.5	64.2	48	-0.4	0.1	-0.5	1
8016	1933-06-20	CAPE DORSET	NU	2400637	-76.5	64.2	48	-0.4	0.1	-0.5	1
8017	1933-09-04	CAPE DORSET	NU	2400637	-76.5	64.2	48	0.9	1.3	-0.4	1
8018	1933-09-30	CAPE DORSET	NU	2400637	-76.5	64.2	48	-1.3	-1	-0.3	1
8019	1933-10-08	CAPE DORSET	NU	2400637	-76.5	64.2	48	-0.9	-0.5	-0.4	1
8020	1934-08-21	CAPE DORSET	NU	2400637	-76.5	64.2	48	0.9	1.8	-0.9	1
8021	1934-09-12	CAPE DORSET	NU	2400637	-76.5	64.2	48	-0.9	-0.5	-0.4	1
8022	1935-06-08	CAPE DORSET	NU	2400637	-76.5	64.2	48	-1.5	-1	-0.5	1
8023	1937-06-04	CAPE DORSET	NU	2400637	-76.5	64.2	48	-1.3	-1	-0.3	1

8024	1937-07-07	CAPE DORSET	NU	2400637	-76.5	64.2	48	-0.9	-0.5	-0.4	1
8025	1937-07-20	CAPE DORSET	NU	2400637	-76.5	64.2	48	-0.4	0.1	-0.5	1
8026	1937-08-14	CAPE DORSET	NU	2400637	-76.5	64.2	48	2.8	2.9	-0.1	1
8027	1937-08-31	CAPE DORSET	NU	2400637	-76.5	64.2	48	0.2	0.6	-0.4	1
8028	1937-09-06	CAPE DORSET	NU	2400637	-76.5	64.2	48	-0.9	-0.5	-0.4	1
8029	1937-09-24	CAPE DORSET	NU	2400637	-76.5	64.2	48	-0.9	-0.5	-0.4	1
8030	1939-08-25	CAPE DORSET	NU	2400637	-76.5	64.2	48	1.8	2.9	-1.1	1
8031	1939-09-07	CAPE DORSET	NU	2400637	-76.5	64.2	48	0.3	0.6	-0.3	1
8032	1940-10-01	CAPE DORSET	NU	2400637	-76.5	64.2	48	-1.2	-1.1	-0.1	1
8033	1944-06-27	CAPE DORSET	NU	2400637	-76.5	64.2	48	-0.9	0.1	-1	1
8034	1944-07-12	CAPE DORSET	NU	2400637	-76.5	64.2	48	-0.9	-0.5	-0.4	1
8035	1945-10-08	CAPE DORSET	NU	2400637	-76.5	64.2	48	-1.2	-1.1	-0.1	1
8036	1946-06-22	CAPE DORSET	NU	2400637	-76.5	64.2	48	-1.3	-1.1	-0.2	1
8037	1995-02-11	CAPE DORSET	NU	2400637	-76.5	64.2	48	-15	0	-15	1
8038	1995-02-17	CAPE DORSET	NU	2400637	-76.5	64.2	48	-24	0	-24	1
8039	1995-02-24	CAPE DORSET	NU	2400637	-76.5	64.2	48	-28	0	-28	1
8040	1995-02-25	CAPE DORSET	NU	2400637	-76.5	64.2	48	-30	0	-30	1
8041	1995-03-18	CAPE DORSET	NU	2400637	-76.5	64.2	48	-20	0	-20	1
8042	1995-03-25	CAPE DORSET	NU	2400637	-76.5	64.2	48	-10	0	-10	1
8043	1995-04-09	CAPE DORSET	NU	2400637	-76.5	64.2	48	-6	0	-6	1
8044	1995-04-17	CAPE DORSET	NU	2400637	-76.5	64.2	48	-3	0	-3	1
8045	1995-05-07	CAPE DORSET	NU	2400637	-76.5	64.2	48	-2.8	0	-2.8	1
8046	1995-05-14	CAPE DORSET	NU	2400637	-76.5	64.2	48	-1.6	0	-1.6	1
8047	2000-12-24	CAPE DORSET	NU	2400637	-76.5	64.2	48	-13.8	-10	-3.8	1
8048	1916-11-15	GASPE	QUE	7052601	-64.48	48.78	34	-6.7	-6.4	-0.3	1
8049	1918-07-11	GASPE	QUE	7052601	-64.48	48.78	34	13.9	15.1	-1.2	1
8050	1919-02-13	GASPE	QUE	7052601	-64.48	48.78	34	-6.7	-6.5	-0.2	1
8051	1922-03-14	GASPE	QUE	7052601	-64.48	48.78	34	-7.8	-7.7	-0.1	1
8052	1962-12-28	GASPE	QUE	7052601	-64.48	48.78	34	-8.9	-7.9	-1	1
8053	1993-04-26	GASPE	QUE	7052601	-64.48	48.78	34	0.3	0.5	-0.2	1
8054	1914-03-10	WOODSTOCK	NB	8105600	-67.55	46.17	153	-6.5	-5.7	-0.8	1
8055	1914-03-11	WOODSTOCK	NB	8105600	-67.55	46.17	153	-4.7	-4.5	-0.2	1
8056	1914-03-12	WOODSTOCK	NB	8105600	-67.55	46.17	153	-4.8	-3.2	-1.6	1
8057	1915-09-12	WOODSTOCK	NB	8105600	-67.55	46.17	153	19.8	20.4	-0.6	1

8058	1915-12-26	WOODSTOCK	NB	8105600	-67.55	46.17	153	-2.9	-2.8	-0.1	1
8059	1918-01-18	WOODSTOCK	NB	8105600	-67.55	46.17	153	-8.2	-7.8	-0.4	1
8060	1918-02-07	WOODSTOCK	NB	8105600	-67.55	46.17	153	-21	-20.5	-0.5	1
8061	1920-12-12	WOODSTOCK	NB	8105600	-67.55	46.17	153	0.1	0.3	-0.2	1
8062	1922-11-19	WOODSTOCK	NB	8105600	-67.55	46.17	153	0.7	0.9	-0.2	1
8063	1924-04-10	WOODSTOCK	NB	8105600	-67.55	46.17	153	3.3	3.7	-0.4	1
8064	1925-12-04	WOODSTOCK	NB	8105600	-67.55	46.17	153	2.7	3	-0.3	1
8065	1930-12-10	WOODSTOCK	NB	8105600	-67.55	46.17	153	-3	-2.2	-0.8	1
8066	1933-01-13	WOODSTOCK	NB	8105600	-67.55	46.17	153	-1.7	-0.7	-1	1
8067	1933-02-28	WOODSTOCK	NB	8105600	-67.55	46.17	153	4.7	4.8	-0.1	1
8068	1934-12-14	WOODSTOCK	NB	8105600	-67.55	46.17	153	-9.9	-9.1	-0.8	1
8069	1934-12-27	WOODSTOCK	NB	8105600	-67.55	46.17	153	-16	-15	-1	1
8070	1935-01-24	WOODSTOCK	NB	8105600	-67.55	46.17	153	-17.1	-16.9	-0.2	1
8071	1935-02-25	WOODSTOCK	NB	8105600	-67.55	46.17	153	-8.8	-8.4	-0.4	1
8072	1936-01-28	WOODSTOCK	NB	8105600	-67.55	46.17	153	-11	-10.9	-0.1	1
8073	1936-04-16	WOODSTOCK	NB	8105600	-67.55	46.17	153	1.3	1.4	-0.1	1
8074	1936-11-03	WOODSTOCK	NB	8105600	-67.55	46.17	153	-1.7	-1.1	-0.6	1
8075	1936-12-03	WOODSTOCK	NB	8105600	-67.55	46.17	153	0.1	0.8	-0.7	1
8076	1936-12-07	WOODSTOCK	NB	8105600	-67.55	46.17	153	3.7	4.3	-0.6	1
8077	1936-12-12	WOODSTOCK	NB	8105600	-67.55	46.17	153	3.6	4.3	-0.7	1
8078	1937-01-08	WOODSTOCK	NB	8105600	-67.55	46.17	153	-2.4	-1.7	-0.7	1
8079	1937-01-09	WOODSTOCK	NB	8105600	-67.55	46.17	153	-0.5	0.3	-0.8	1
8080	1937-01-14	WOODSTOCK	NB	8105600	-67.55	46.17	153	2.7	4.3	-1.6	1
8081	1937-01-17	WOODSTOCK	NB	8105600	-67.55	46.17	153	4.1	5.3	-1.2	1
8082	1937-12-09	WOODSTOCK	NB	8105600	-67.55	46.17	153	-3.6	-3.2	-0.4	1
8083	1937-12-29	WOODSTOCK	NB	8105600	-67.55	46.17	153	-24.3	-24.2	-0.1	1
8084	1937-12-30	WOODSTOCK	NB	8105600	-67.55	46.17	153	-27.1	-25.3	-1.8	1
8085	1938-02-11	WOODSTOCK	NB	8105600	-67.55	46.17	153	-22.1	-21.5	-0.6	1
8086	1938-02-24	WOODSTOCK	NB	8105600	-67.55	46.17	153	-5.9	-3.8	-2.1	1
8087	1938-12-15	WOODSTOCK	NB	8105600	-67.55	46.17	153	-4.7	-4.4	-0.3	1
8088	1938-12-22	WOODSTOCK	NB	8105600	-67.55	46.17	153	-4.7	-2.8	-1.9	1
8089	1939-02-16	WOODSTOCK	NB	8105600	-67.55	46.17	153	-10.4	-9.7	-0.7	1
8090	1939-11-09	WOODSTOCK	NB	8105600	-67.55	46.17	153	2.3	2.5	-0.2	1
8091	1940-01-15	WOODSTOCK	NB	8105600	-67.55	46.17	153	-4.7	-3.8	-0.9	1

8092	1940-01-16	WOODSTOCK	NB	8105600	-67.55	46.17	153	1.8	2.5	-0.7	1
8093	1941-01-03	WOODSTOCK	NB	8105600	-67.55	46.17	153	-4.1	-3.8	-0.3	1
8094	1941-01-04	WOODSTOCK	NB	8105600	-67.55	46.17	153	-5.3	-5	-0.3	1
8095	1941-01-19	WOODSTOCK	NB	8105600	-67.55	46.17	153	-4.7	-3.8	-0.9	1
8096	1941-03-17	WOODSTOCK	NB	8105600	-67.55	46.17	153	0.2	1.4	-1.2	1
8097	1941-12-07	WOODSTOCK	NB	8105600	-67.55	46.17	153	-2.9	-2.7	-0.2	1
8098	1941-12-25	WOODSTOCK	NB	8105600	-67.55	46.17	153	3.7	4.3	-0.6	1
8099	1944-12-08	WOODSTOCK	NB	8105600	-67.55	46.17	153	-0.5	-0.1	-0.4	1
8100	1945-11-04	WOODSTOCK	NB	8105600	-67.55	46.17	153	3.6	4.8	-1.2	1
8101	1945-11-15	WOODSTOCK	NB	8105600	-67.55	46.17	153	-2.9	-2.8	-0.1	1
8102	1946-12-22	WOODSTOCK	NB	8105600	-67.55	46.17	153	-6.5	-5.8	-0.7	1
8103	1946-12-29	WOODSTOCK	NB	8105600	-67.55	46.17	153	-1.7	-1.1	-0.6	1
8104	1947-01-08	WOODSTOCK	NB	8105600	-67.55	46.17	153	-7.7	-6.5	-1.2	1
8105	1947-02-18	WOODSTOCK	NB	8105600	-67.55	46.17	153	-2.9	-2.2	-0.7	1
8106	1947-04-12	WOODSTOCK	NB	8105600	-67.55	46.17	153	4.7	5.3	-0.6	1
8107	1949-01-29	WOODSTOCK	NB	8105600	-67.55	46.17	153	-2.9	-2.8	-0.1	1
8108	1949-12-30	WOODSTOCK	NB	8105600	-67.55	46.17	153	-1.7	-0.1	-1.6	1
8109	1950-01-05	WOODSTOCK	NB	8105600	-67.55	46.17	153	2.3	3.1	-0.8	1
8110	1950-01-08	WOODSTOCK	NB	8105600	-67.55	46.17	153	-23.2	-21.5	-1.7	1
8111	1950-01-17	WOODSTOCK	NB	8105600	-67.55	46.17	153	-11	-10.9	-0.1	1
8112	1950-01-30	WOODSTOCK	NB	8105600	-67.55	46.17	153	0.1	0.9	-0.8	1
8113	1950-02-20	WOODSTOCK	NB	8105600	-67.55	46.17	153	-15.4	-14.6	-0.8	1
8114	1951-01-13	WOODSTOCK	NB	8105600	-67.55	46.17	153	-3.6	-3.2	-0.4	1
8115	1951-01-15	WOODSTOCK	NB	8105600	-67.55	46.17	153	1.8	2.5	-0.7	1
8116	1951-10-24	WOODSTOCK	NB	8105600	-67.55	46.17	153	8.9	9.1	-0.2	1
8117	1951-12-08	WOODSTOCK	NB	8105600	-67.55	46.17	153	3.6	3.7	-0.1	1
8118	1951-12-10	WOODSTOCK	NB	8105600	-67.55	46.17	153	-2.9	-2.8	-0.1	1
8119	1951-12-21	WOODSTOCK	NB	8105600	-67.55	46.17	153	-2.9	-2.8	-0.1	1
8120	1952-01-21	WOODSTOCK	NB	8105600	-67.55	46.17	153	-5.9	-4.5	-1.4	1
8121	1952-12-12	WOODSTOCK	NB	8105600	-67.55	46.17	153	0.7	0.9	-0.2	1
8122	1953-01-12	WOODSTOCK	NB	8105600	-67.55	46.17	153	-2.4	-0.7	-1.7	1
8123	1953-01-14	WOODSTOCK	NB	8105600	-67.55	46.17	153	-6.5	-5.7	-0.8	1
8124	1953-01-25	WOODSTOCK	NB	8105600	-67.55	46.17	153	4.7	5.2	-0.5	1
8125	1953-01-29	WOODSTOCK	NB	8105600	-67.55	46.17	153	0.2	0.9	-0.7	1

8126	1953-02-09	WOODSTOCK	NB	8105600	-67.55	46.17	153	0.2	0.3	-0.1	1
8127	1953-02-16	WOODSTOCK	NB	8105600	-67.55	46.17	153	1.3	1.4	-0.1	1
8128	1953-02-22	WOODSTOCK	NB	8105600	-67.55	46.17	153	-0.5	-0.1	-0.4	1
8129	1953-03-13	WOODSTOCK	NB	8105600	-67.55	46.17	153	-2.4	-2.2	-0.2	1
8130	1953-11-05	WOODSTOCK	NB	8105600	-67.55	46.17	153	-2.4	-1.7	-0.7	1
8131	1953-11-07	WOODSTOCK	NB	8105600	-67.55	46.17	153	3.6	4.9	-1.3	1
8132	1954-01-17	WOODSTOCK	NB	8105600	-67.55	46.17	153	-16	-15	-1	1
8133	1954-01-27	WOODSTOCK	NB	8105600	-67.55	46.17	153	-7.7	-7.1	-0.6	1
8134	1954-02-05	WOODSTOCK	NB	8105600	-67.55	46.17	153	1.8	2.5	-0.7	1
8135	1954-02-07	WOODSTOCK	NB	8105600	-67.55	46.17	153	-6.5	-5.7	-0.8	1
8136	1954-11-22	WOODSTOCK	NB	8105600	-67.55	46.17	153	3.6	4.3	-0.7	1
8137	1955-01-08	WOODSTOCK	NB	8105600	-67.55	46.17	153	0.7	0.9	-0.2	1
8138	1955-03-17	WOODSTOCK	NB	8105600	-67.55	46.17	153	-2.4	-1.1	-1.3	1
8139	1955-05-08	WOODSTOCK	NB	8105600	-67.55	46.17	153	3.6	3.7	-0.1	1
8140	1955-12-05	WOODSTOCK	NB	8105600	-67.55	46.17	153	-2.4	-1.1	-1.3	1
8141	1955-12-19	WOODSTOCK	NB	8105600	-67.55	46.17	153	-21.6	-21.5	-0.1	1
8142	1956-01-06	WOODSTOCK	NB	8105600	-67.55	46.17	153	-3.6	-2.8	-0.8	1
8143	1956-01-10	WOODSTOCK	NB	8105600	-67.55	46.17	153	3.3	4.2	-0.9	1
8144	1956-01-14	WOODSTOCK	NB	8105600	-67.55	46.17	153	1.3	1.8	-0.5	1
8145	1956-01-15	WOODSTOCK	NB	8105600	-67.55	46.17	153	-0.5	-0.1	-0.4	1
8146	1956-01-18	WOODSTOCK	NB	8105600	-67.55	46.17	153	-2.9	-2.2	-0.7	1
8147	1956-02-16	WOODSTOCK	NB	8105600	-67.55	46.17	153	-10.4	-9.1	-1.3	1
8148	1956-02-26	WOODSTOCK	NB	8105600	-67.55	46.17	153	-5.9	-5.8	-0.1	1
8149	1956-03-03	WOODSTOCK	NB	8105600	-67.55	46.17	153	0.2	0.9	-0.7	1
8150	1956-03-04	WOODSTOCK	NB	8105600	-67.55	46.17	153	-1.7	-0.7	-1	1
8151	1956-12-14	WOODSTOCK	NB	8105600	-67.55	46.17	153	-5.3	-3.2	-2.1	1
8152	1957-01-31	WOODSTOCK	NB	8105600	-67.55	46.17	153	-8.8	-7.8	-1	1
8153	1958-01-02	WOODSTOCK	NB	8105600	-67.55	46.17	153	-2.9	-1.1	-1.8	1
8154	1958-12-07	WOODSTOCK	NB	8105600	-67.55	46.17	153	-6.5	-4.4	-2.1	1
8155	1959-02-08	WOODSTOCK	NB	8105600	-67.55	46.17	153	-17.7	-16.5	-1.2	1
8156	1959-02-15	WOODSTOCK	NB	8105600	-67.55	46.17	153	-5.9	-5.8	-0.1	1
8157	1959-02-19	WOODSTOCK	NB	8105600	-67.55	46.17	153	-9.3	-9.1	-0.2	1
8158	1959-03-22	WOODSTOCK	NB	8105600	-67.55	46.17	153	-9.9	-9.8	-0.1	1
8159	1959-12-16	WOODSTOCK	NB	8105600	-67.55	46.17	153	-3.6	-2.7	-0.9	1

8160	1960-01-03	WOODSTOCK	NB	8105600	-67.55	46.17	153	1.3	1.8	-0.5	1
8161	1960-01-07	WOODSTOCK	NB	8105600	-67.55	46.17	153	-14.9	-14.6	-0.3	1
8162	1960-02-12	WOODSTOCK	NB	8105600	-67.55	46.17	153	0.2	1.4	-1.2	1
8163	1960-03-08	WOODSTOCK	NB	8105600	-67.55	46.17	153	-4.1	-2.2	-1.9	1
8164	1960-11-30	WOODSTOCK	NB	8105600	-67.55	46.17	153	3.6	4.9	-1.3	1
8165	1960-12-17	WOODSTOCK	NB	8105600	-67.55	46.17	153	-2.9	-1.1	-1.8	1
8166	1960-12-27	WOODSTOCK	NB	8105600	-67.55	46.17	153	-9.3	-9	-0.3	1
8167	1961-02-20	WOODSTOCK	NB	8105600	-67.55	46.17	153	-2.9	-1.1	-1.8	1
8168	1961-03-30	WOODSTOCK	NB	8105600	-67.55	46.17	153	1.3	1.4	-0.1	1
8169	1961-10-15	WOODSTOCK	NB	8105600	-67.55	46.17	153	4.7	5.8	-1.1	1
8170	1961-11-07	WOODSTOCK	NB	8105600	-67.55	46.17	153	4.7	5.2	-0.5	1
8171	1961-11-19	WOODSTOCK	NB	8105600	-67.55	46.17	153	-1.7	-0.7	-1	1
8172	1961-12-02	WOODSTOCK	NB	8105600	-67.55	46.17	153	-1.7	-1.1	-0.6	1
8173	1962-02-10	WOODSTOCK	NB	8105600	-67.55	46.17	153	-13.8	-13.2	-0.6	1
8174	1962-02-18	WOODSTOCK	NB	8105600	-67.55	46.17	153	-8.2	-5.7	-2.5	1
8175	1962-03-01	WOODSTOCK	NB	8105600	-67.55	46.17	153	-1.7	-1.1	-0.6	1
8176	1962-11-06	WOODSTOCK	NB	8105600	-67.55	46.17	153	0.7	1.4	-0.7	1
8177	1962-11-23	WOODSTOCK	NB	8105600	-67.55	46.17	153	1.3	1.4	-0.1	1
8178	1962-12-20	WOODSTOCK	NB	8105600	-67.55	46.17	153	-12.7	-12.4	-0.3	1
8179	1963-01-21	WOODSTOCK	NB	8105600	-67.55	46.17	153	-4.1	-2.2	-1.9	1
8180	1963-01-28	WOODSTOCK	NB	8105600	-67.55	46.17	153	-12.7	-11.8	-0.9	1
8181	1963-10-04	WOODSTOCK	NB	8105600	-67.55	46.17	153	7.1	7.4	-0.3	1
8182	1963-10-29	WOODSTOCK	NB	8105600	-67.55	46.17	153	2.3	3.1	-0.8	1
8183	1963-11-09	WOODSTOCK	NB	8105600	-67.55	46.17	153	7.1	7.4	-0.3	1
8184	1963-11-24	WOODSTOCK	NB	8105600	-67.55	46.17	153	2.7	4.3	-1.6	1
8185	1963-12-16	WOODSTOCK	NB	8105600	-67.55	46.17	153	-12.7	-12.4	-0.3	1
8186	1963-12-19	WOODSTOCK	NB	8105600	-67.55	46.17	153	-16.6	-16.5	-0.1	1
8187	1963-12-26	WOODSTOCK	NB	8105600	-67.55	46.17	153	-14.9	-14.6	-0.3	1
8188	1964-01-11	WOODSTOCK	NB	8105600	-67.55	46.17	153	-13.2	-12.7	-0.5	1
8189	1964-01-22	WOODSTOCK	NB	8105600	-67.55	46.17	153	1.3	2.5	-1.2	1
8190	1964-11-26	WOODSTOCK	NB	8105600	-67.55	46.17	153	4.7	6.2	-1.5	1
8191	1964-11-29	WOODSTOCK	NB	8105600	-67.55	46.17	153	-1.7	-1.1	-0.6	1
8192	1964-12-01	WOODSTOCK	NB	8105600	-67.55	46.17	153	-7.7	-5.8	-1.9	1
8193	1964-12-18	WOODSTOCK	NB	8105600	-67.55	46.17	153	-4.8	-2.8	-2	1

8194	1964-12-29	WOODSTOCK	NB	8105600	-67.55	46.17	153	-5.9	-5	-0.9	1
8195	1970-12-04	WOODSTOCK	NB	8105600	-67.55	46.17	153	-7	-6.4	-0.6	1
8196	1970-12-27	WOODSTOCK	NB	8105600	-67.55	46.17	153	-6.5	-5.7	-0.8	1
8197	1972-01-26	WOODSTOCK	NB	8105600	-67.55	46.17	153	-23.2	-21.5	-1.7	1
8198	1974-11-25	WOODSTOCK	NB	8105600	-67.55	46.17	153	1.3	1.4	-0.1	1
8199	1974-12-04	WOODSTOCK	NB	8105600	-67.55	46.17	153	-4.8	-4.4	-0.4	1
8200	1974-12-24	WOODSTOCK	NB	8105600	-67.55	46.17	153	-2.4	-2.2	-0.2	1
8201	1975-01-13	WOODSTOCK	NB	8105600	-67.55	46.17	153	-0.5	0.3	-0.8	1
8202	1975-01-20	WOODSTOCK	NB	8105600	-67.55	46.17	153	-21.6	-21.5	-0.1	1
8203	1975-12-03	WOODSTOCK	NB	8105600	-67.55	46.17	153	-3.6	-3.2	-0.4	1
8204	1975-12-19	WOODSTOCK	NB	8105600	-67.55	46.17	153	-17.7	-17.4	-0.3	1
8205	1975-12-24	WOODSTOCK	NB	8105600	-67.55	46.17	153	-22.1	-21.5	-0.6	1
8206	1976-01-23	WOODSTOCK	NB	8105600	-67.55	46.17	153	-24.9	-23.7	-1.2	1
8207	1976-05-07	WOODSTOCK	NB	8105600	-67.55	46.17	153	3.6	4.3	-0.7	1
8208	1976-11-06	WOODSTOCK	NB	8105600	-67.55	46.17	153	2.3	2.5	-0.2	1
8209	1976-11-29	WOODSTOCK	NB	8105600	-67.55	46.17	153	-0.5	-0.1	-0.4	1
8210	1979-03-11	WOODSTOCK	NB	8105600	-67.55	46.17	153	0.6	0.9	-0.3	1
8211	1979-12-27	WOODSTOCK	NB	8105600	-67.55	46.17	153	-0.5	0.9	-1.4	1
8212	1980-11-25	WOODSTOCK	NB	8105600	-67.55	46.17	153	3.7	4.5	-0.8	1
8213	1980-12-07	WOODSTOCK	NB	8105600	-67.55	46.17	153	-4.9	-4.3	-0.6	1
8214	1981-11-17	WOODSTOCK	NB	8105600	-67.55	46.17	153	3.7	3.9	-0.2	1
8215	1981-11-23	WOODSTOCK	NB	8105600	-67.55	46.17	153	-0.5	0	-0.5	1
8216	1981-11-24	WOODSTOCK	NB	8105600	-67.55	46.17	153	-1	-0.9	-0.1	1
8217	1981-11-29	WOODSTOCK	NB	8105600	-67.55	46.17	153	-4.3	-3.8	-0.5	1
8218	1981-12-12	WOODSTOCK	NB	8105600	-67.55	46.17	153	-1.6	-1.4	-0.2	1
8219	1982-10-08	WOODSTOCK	NB	8105600	-67.55	46.17	153	6.1	6.2	-0.1	1
8220	1982-12-12	WOODSTOCK	NB	8105600	-67.55	46.17	153	-16	-15.8	-0.2	1
8221	1983-01-13	WOODSTOCK	NB	8105600	-67.55	46.17	153	-5.4	-4.9	-0.5	1
8222	1983-03-23	WOODSTOCK	NB	8105600	-67.55	46.17	153	-2.1	-1.9	-0.2	1
8223	1983-04-08	WOODSTOCK	NB	8105600	-67.55	46.17	153	5.6	5.7	-0.1	1
8224	1983-11-04	WOODSTOCK	NB	8105600	-67.55	46.17	153	2.5	2.8	-0.3	1
8225	1984-01-06	WOODSTOCK	NB	8105600	-67.55	46.17	153	0	0.4	-0.4	1
8226	1984-01-08	WOODSTOCK	NB	8105600	-67.55	46.17	153	-14.5	-14.1	-0.4	1
8227	1984-02-21	WOODSTOCK	NB	8105600	-67.55	46.17	153	-3.3	-2.8	-0.5	1

8228	1984-04-08	WOODSTOCK	NB	8105600	-67.55	46.17	153	-1.6	-0.9	-0.7	1
8229	1984-11-13	WOODSTOCK	NB	8105600	-67.55	46.17	153	3.3	3.9	-0.6	1
8230	1984-11-14	WOODSTOCK	NB	8105600	-67.55	46.17	153	-0.5	-0.1	-0.4	1
8231	1985-11-11	WOODSTOCK	NB	8105600	-67.55	46.17	153	-2.1	-1.9	-0.2	1
8232	1985-11-15	WOODSTOCK	NB	8105600	-67.55	46.17	153	-4.3	-3.8	-0.5	1
8233	1990-04-10	WOODSTOCK	NB	8105600	-67.55	46.17	153	2.5	2.8	-0.3	1
8234	1992-12-04	WOODSTOCK	NB	8105600	-67.55	46.17	153	-0.5	0	-0.5	1
8235	1994-04-07	WOODSTOCK	NB	8105600	-67.55	46.17	153	1.1	1.3	-0.2	1
8236	1995-11-08	WOODSTOCK	NB	8105600	-67.55	46.17	153	3.7	3.9	-0.2	1
8237	1996-02-26	WOODSTOCK	NB	8105600	-67.55	46.17	153	-1	-0.5	-0.5	1
8238	1994-02-19	SHINGLE POINT	YT	2100950	-137.22	68.95	49	-33.5	-27.1	-6.4	1
8239	1994-02-20	SHINGLE POINT	YT	2100950	-137.22	68.95	49	-33.1	-30	-3.1	1
8240	1994-04-18	SHINGLE POINT	YT	2100950	-137.22	68.95	49	-19.1	-19	-0.1	1
8241	1994-09-16	SHINGLE POINT	YT	2100950	-137.22	68.95	49	-2.1	-1.9	-0.2	1
8242	1994-11-25	SHINGLE POINT	YT	2100950	-137.22	68.95	49	-27.9	-22.5	-5.4	1
8243	2010-04-26	SHINGLE POINT	YT	2100950	-137.22	68.95	49	-6.3	-3.7	-2.6	1
8244	1988-04-18	CHESTERFIELD	NU	2300707	-90.72	63.33	10	-3	-2.5	-0.5	1
8245	1990-11-26	CHESTERFIELD	NU	2300707	-90.72	63.33	10	-24	-18	-6	1
8246	1990-11-27	CHESTERFIELD	NU	2300707	-90.72	63.33	10	-27	-20.5	-6.5	1
8247	1990-11-28	CHESTERFIELD	NU	2300707	-90.72	63.33	10	-28.5	-25	-3.5	1
8248	2007-02-08	CHESTERFIELD	NU	2300707	-90.72	63.33	10	-30.5	-26.5	-4	1
8249	2007-02-17	CHESTERFIELD	NU	2300707	-90.72	63.33	10	-27.5	-26	-1.5	1
8250	2009-02-23	CHESTERFIELD	NU	2300707	-90.72	63.33	10	-35.5	-35	-0.5	1
8251	2010-12-15	CHESTERFIELD	NU	2300707	-90.72	63.33	10	-12.5	-12.4	-0.1	1
8252	2010-12-19	CHESTERFIELD	NU	2300707	-90.72	63.33	10	0	0.2	-0.2	1
8253	2010-12-20	CHESTERFIELD	NU	2300707	-90.72	63.33	10	-3.6	-3	-0.6	1
8254	2010-12-21	CHESTERFIELD	NU	2300707	-90.72	63.33	10	-6.5	-3.5	-3	1
8255	2010-12-22	CHESTERFIELD	NU	2300707	-90.72	63.33	10	-13.7	-6.5	-7.2	1
8256	2010-12-29	CHESTERFIELD	NU	2300707	-90.72	63.33	10	-15	-9.7	-5.3	1
8257	2010-12-31	CHESTERFIELD	NU	2300707	-90.72	63.33	10	-14	-9.5	-4.5	1
8258	2012-10-11	CHESTERFIELD	NU	2300707	-90.72	63.33	10	-5	-2.5	-2.5	1
8259	2012-10-12	CHESTERFIELD	NU	2300707	-90.72	63.33	10	-5.5	-3	-2.5	1
8260	2012-10-13	CHESTERFIELD	NU	2300707	-90.72	63.33	10	-5	-4.8	-0.2	1
8261	2012-10-14	CHESTERFIELD	NU	2300707	-90.72	63.33	10	-5	-3.8	-1.2	1

8262	2012-10-15	CHESTERFIELD	NU	2300707	-90.72	63.33	10	-5.6	-2.5	-3.1	1
8263	2012-11-17	CHESTERFIELD	NU	2300707	-90.72	63.33	10	-21.6	-21.2	-0.4	1
8264	2012-11-18	CHESTERFIELD	NU	2300707	-90.72	63.33	10	-20.1	-16.5	-3.6	1
8265	2012-11-19	CHESTERFIELD	NU	2300707	-90.72	63.33	10	-16	-12.5	-3.5	1
8266	2012-11-20	CHESTERFIELD	NU	2300707	-90.72	63.33	10	-16	-13.5	-2.5	1
8267	2012-11-21	CHESTERFIELD	NU	2300707	-90.72	63.33	10	-2.4	-2	-0.4	1
8268	2012-11-30	CHESTERFIELD	NU	2300707	-90.72	63.33	10	-34.5	-28	-6.5	1
8269	1908-01-01	SION	ALTA	3015960	-114.12	53.88	701	-26	-25.4	-0.6	1
8270	1908-01-14	SION	ALTA	3015960	-114.12	53.88	701	-17.4	-15.9	-1.5	1
8271	1908-01-30	SION	ALTA	3015960	-114.12	53.88	701	-10.6	-10.3	-0.3	1
8272	1908-03-11	SION	ALTA	3015960	-114.12	53.88	701	-5.1	-4.3	-0.8	1
8273	1911-01-09	SION	ALTA	3015960	-114.12	53.88	701	-32.6	-29.5	-3.1	1
8274	1911-01-23	SION	ALTA	3015960	-114.12	53.88	701	-21.5	-20	-1.5	1
8275	1911-01-30	SION	ALTA	3015960	-114.12	53.88	701	-24.3	-23.1	-1.2	1
8276	1911-02-01	SION	ALTA	3015960	-114.12	53.88	701	-24.3	-23.2	-1.1	1
8277	1911-12-23	SION	ALTA	3015960	-114.12	53.88	701	-16.3	-15.8	-0.5	1
8278	1911-12-27	SION	ALTA	3015960	-114.12	53.88	701	-21.5	-21.3	-0.2	1
8279	1911-12-28	SION	ALTA	3015960	-114.12	53.88	701	-29.9	-27.9	-2	1
8280	1911-12-30	SION	ALTA	3015960	-114.12	53.88	701	-26	-24.9	-1.1	1
8281	1912-01-01	SION	ALTA	3015960	-114.12	53.88	701	-12.9	-10.3	-2.6	1
8282	1912-11-30	SION	ALTA	3015960	-114.12	53.88	701	-16.3	-12.9	-3.4	1
8283	1913-01-30	SION	ALTA	3015960	-114.12	53.88	701	-15.3	-14.5	-0.8	1
8284	1913-03-12	SION	ALTA	3015960	-114.12	53.88	701	-10.6	-9.7	-0.9	1
8285	1913-07-02	SION	ALTA	3015960	-114.12	53.88	701	9.6	9.9	-0.3	1
8286	1914-02-01	SION	ALTA	3015960	-114.12	53.88	701	-19	-16.6	-2.4	1
8287	1914-02-12	SION	ALTA	3015960	-114.12	53.88	701	-13.8	-13	-0.8	1
8288	1914-11-13	SION	ALTA	3015960	-114.12	53.88	701	-10.5	-10.1	-0.4	1
8289	1914-11-15	SION	ALTA	3015960	-114.12	53.88	701	-10.5	-9.4	-1.1	1
8290	1915-07-14	SION	ALTA	3015960	-114.12	53.88	701	7.6	8.9	-1.3	1
8291	1915-12-11	SION	ALTA	3015960	-114.12	53.88	701	-11.4	-10.3	-1.1	1
8292	1915-12-28	SION	ALTA	3015960	-114.12	53.88	701	-11.4	-10.3	-1.1	1
8293	1916-01-04	SION	ALTA	3015960	-114.12	53.88	701	-26	-25.8	-0.2	1
8294	1916-01-09	SION	ALTA	3015960	-114.12	53.88	701	-27.1	-26.4	-0.7	1
8295	1916-01-21	SION	ALTA	3015960	-114.12	53.88	701	-31	-26.4	-4.6	1

8296	1916-11-10	SION	ALTA	3015960	-114.12	53.88	701	-12.4	-10.2	-2.2	1
8297	1916-12-19	SION	ALTA	3015960	-114.12	53.88	701	-20	-19.2	-0.8	1
8298	1917-01-09	SION	ALTA	3015960	-114.12	53.88	701	-0.3	0.3	-0.6	1
8299	1917-01-23	SION	ALTA	3015960	-114.12	53.88	701	-24.3	-21.6	-2.7	1
8300	1917-01-27	SION	ALTA	3015960	-114.12	53.88	701	-19.4	-19.3	-0.1	1
8301	1917-12-23	SION	ALTA	3015960	-114.12	53.88	701	-28.2	-26.9	-1.3	1
8302	1917-12-25	SION	ALTA	3015960	-114.12	53.88	701	-29.3	-26.4	-2.9	1
8303	1918-02-01	SION	ALTA	3015960	-114.12	53.88	701	-10.5	-9.4	-1.1	1
8304	1919-10-20	SION	ALTA	3015960	-114.12	53.88	701	0.6	1.2	-0.6	1
8305	1919-10-21	SION	ALTA	3015960	-114.12	53.88	701	-1.3	-0.8	-0.5	1
8306	1919-12-15	SION	ALTA	3015960	-114.12	53.88	701	-21.5	-19.3	-2.2	1
8307	1920-01-17	SION	ALTA	3015960	-114.12	53.88	701	-24.3	-22.6	-1.7	1
8308	1920-01-18	SION	ALTA	3015960	-114.12	53.88	701	-23.2	-23	-0.2	1
8309	1920-09-25	SION	ALTA	3015960	-114.12	53.88	701	1.1	1.2	-0.1	1
8310	1920-12-17	SION	ALTA	3015960	-114.12	53.88	701	-11.9	-11.2	-0.7	1
8311	1920-12-18	SION	ALTA	3015960	-114.12	53.88	701	-11.1	-10.3	-0.8	1
8312	1921-01-16	SION	ALTA	3015960	-114.12	53.88	701	-21.1	-19.7	-1.4	1
8313	1921-02-14	SION	ALTA	3015960	-114.12	53.88	701	-13.9	-11.8	-2.1	1
8314	1921-02-15	SION	ALTA	3015960	-114.12	53.88	701	-11.9	-11.8	-0.1	1
8315	1921-02-17	SION	ALTA	3015960	-114.12	53.88	701	-15.4	-13.7	-1.7	1
8316	1921-03-06	SION	ALTA	3015960	-114.12	53.88	701	0.2	0.5	-0.3	1
8317	1921-03-29	SION	ALTA	3015960	-114.12	53.88	701	-6.7	-6.5	-0.2	1
8318	1921-11-19	SION	ALTA	3015960	-114.12	53.88	701	-21.5	-21	-0.5	1
8319	1921-11-26	SION	ALTA	3015960	-114.12	53.88	701	-1.9	-1.5	-0.4	1
8320	1921-12-18	SION	ALTA	3015960	-114.12	53.88	701	-27.1	-25.4	-1.7	1
8321	1922-10-31	SION	ALTA	3015960	-114.12	53.88	701	-2.3	-2.2	-0.1	1
8322	1922-11-17	SION	ALTA	3015960	-114.12	53.88	701	-10.5	-9.6	-0.9	1
8323	1922-12-07	SION	ALTA	3015960	-114.12	53.88	701	-19.4	-19.2	-0.2	1
8324	1922-12-13	SION	ALTA	3015960	-114.12	53.88	701	-12.4	-9.9	-2.5	1
8325	1922-12-31	SION	ALTA	3015960	-114.12	53.88	701	-14.8	-11.2	-3.6	1
8326	1923-01-03	SION	ALTA	3015960	-114.12	53.88	701	-14.8	-14.5	-0.3	1
8327	1923-01-04	SION	ALTA	3015960	-114.12	53.88	701	-13.8	-13.1	-0.7	1
8328	1923-02-01	SION	ALTA	3015960	-114.12	53.88	701	-13.3	-13.1	-0.2	1
8329	1923-02-09	SION	ALTA	3015960	-114.12	53.88	701	-10.6	-9.9	-0.7	1

8330	1923-02-11	SION	ALTA	3015960	-114.12	53.88	701	-25.4	-24	-1.4	1
8331	1924-02-16	SION	ALTA	3015960	-114.12	53.88	701	-17.4	-17.2	-0.2	1
8332	1924-11-06	SION	ALTA	3015960	-114.12	53.88	701	-11.4	-10.7	-0.7	1
8333	1924-12-14	SION	ALTA	3015960	-114.12	53.88	701	-27.1	-24	-3.1	1
8334	1924-12-23	SION	ALTA	3015960	-114.12	53.88	701	-25.4	-22.3	-3.1	1
8335	1924-12-24	SION	ALTA	3015960	-114.12	53.88	701	-23.8	-23.4	-0.4	1
8336	1924-12-28	SION	ALTA	3015960	-114.12	53.88	701	-27.1	-23.9	-3.2	1
8337	1924-12-29	SION	ALTA	3015960	-114.12	53.88	701	-23.8	-21.6	-2.2	1
8338	1924-12-31	SION	ALTA	3015960	-114.12	53.88	701	-24.9	-23.9	-1	1
8339	1925-01-10	SION	ALTA	3015960	-114.12	53.88	701	-22.6	-21.6	-1	1
8340	1925-01-12	SION	ALTA	3015960	-114.12	53.88	701	-19	-17.2	-1.8	1
8341	1925-01-14	SION	ALTA	3015960	-114.12	53.88	701	-19.4	-18.3	-1.1	1
8342	1925-01-29	SION	ALTA	3015960	-114.12	53.88	701	-20.5	-18.9	-1.6	1
8343	1925-02-14	SION	ALTA	3015960	-114.12	53.88	701	-19	-17.2	-1.8	1
8344	1925-02-24	SION	ALTA	3015960	-114.12	53.88	701	-21.1	-19.7	-1.4	1
8345	1925-09-17	SION	ALTA	3015960	-114.12	53.88	701	1	1.5	-0.5	1
8346	1925-12-20	SION	ALTA	3015960	-114.12	53.88	701	-11.4	-10.1	-1.3	1
8347	1925-12-21	SION	ALTA	3015960	-114.12	53.88	701	-10.1	-9.6	-0.5	1
8348	1925-12-22	SION	ALTA	3015960	-114.12	53.88	701	-11.4	-10.1	-1.3	1
8349	1925-12-25	SION	ALTA	3015960	-114.12	53.88	701	-15.3	-14.5	-0.8	1
8350	1926-01-18	SION	ALTA	3015960	-114.12	53.88	701	-11.4	-9.9	-1.5	1
8351	1926-10-07	SION	ALTA	3015960	-114.12	53.88	701	1.5	2.1	-0.6	1
8352	1926-11-18	SION	ALTA	3015960	-114.12	53.88	701	-11.4	-9.4	-2	1
8353	1926-11-22	SION	ALTA	3015960	-114.12	53.88	701	-10.1	-9.7	-0.4	1
8354	1926-11-23	SION	ALTA	3015960	-114.12	53.88	701	-11.4	-9.5	-1.9	1
8355	1926-11-24	SION	ALTA	3015960	-114.12	53.88	701	-12.4	-10.4	-2	1
8356	1926-12-02	SION	ALTA	3015960	-114.12	53.88	701	-19.4	-18.3	-1.1	1
8357	1926-12-13	SION	ALTA	3015960	-114.12	53.88	701	-21.5	-21.2	-0.3	1
8358	1926-12-14	SION	ALTA	3015960	-114.12	53.88	701	-18.4	-18.3	-0.1	1
8359	1926-12-19	SION	ALTA	3015960	-114.12	53.88	701	-19	-16.7	-2.3	1
8360	1926-12-20	SION	ALTA	3015960	-114.12	53.88	701	-16.3	-14.5	-1.8	1
8361	1927-01-11	SION	ALTA	3015960	-114.12	53.88	701	-10.6	-9.4	-1.2	1
8362	1927-07-02	SION	ALTA	3015960	-114.12	53.88	701	9.6	9.9	-0.3	1
8363	1927-12-03	SION	ALTA	3015960	-114.12	53.88	701	-19	-17.9	-1.1	1

8364	1927-12-09	SION	ALTA	3015960	-114.12	53.88	701	-21.5	-21.1	-0.4	1
8365	1927-12-10	SION	ALTA	3015960	-114.12	53.88	701	-13.3	-13	-0.3	1
8366	1927-12-28	SION	ALTA	3015960	-114.12	53.88	701	-21.5	-21.1	-0.4	1
8367	1928-03-26	SION	ALTA	3015960	-114.12	53.88	701	1.1	1.6	-0.5	1
8368	1928-05-07	SION	ALTA	3015960	-114.12	53.88	701	0.9	2.2	-1.3	1
8369	1929-01-18	SION	ALTA	3015960	-114.12	53.88	701	-21.1	-20.2	-0.9	1
8370	1929-09-23	SION	ALTA	3015960	-114.12	53.88	701	0.9	1.6	-0.7	1
8371	1929-12-14	SION	ALTA	3015960	-114.12	53.88	701	-17.4	-16.7	-0.7	1
8372	1929-12-18	SION	ALTA	3015960	-114.12	53.88	701	-18.4	-18.3	-0.1	1
8373	1930-01-19	SION	ALTA	3015960	-114.12	53.88	701	-18.4	-17.8	-0.6	1
8374	1932-02-01	SION	ALTA	3015960	-114.12	53.88	701	-23.2	-23	-0.2	1
8375	1932-04-23	SION	ALTA	3015960	-114.12	53.88	701	2	2.2	-0.2	1
8376	1933-03-07	SION	ALTA	3015960	-114.12	53.88	701	-11.1	-9.7	-1.4	1
8377	1933-05-16	SION	ALTA	3015960	-114.12	53.88	701	1.5	1.8	-0.3	1
8378	1933-11-14	SION	ALTA	3015960	-114.12	53.88	701	-0.3	0.8	-1.1	1
8379	1933-12-07	SION	ALTA	3015960	-114.12	53.88	701	-18.4	-15.8	-2.6	1
8380	1933-12-14	SION	ALTA	3015960	-114.12	53.88	701	-18.4	-17.8	-0.6	1
8381	1933-12-17	SION	ALTA	3015960	-114.12	53.88	701	-20.5	-19.3	-1.2	1
8382	1933-12-31	SION	ALTA	3015960	-114.12	53.88	701	-29.9	-27.9	-2	1
8383	1934-01-01	SION	ALTA	3015960	-114.12	53.88	701	-27.1	-26.9	-0.2	1
8384	1934-05-01	SION	ALTA	3015960	-114.12	53.88	701	-0.3	0.5	-0.8	1
8385	1934-11-23	SION	ALTA	3015960	-114.12	53.88	701	-10.1	-10	-0.1	1
8386	1935-01-12	SION	ALTA	3015960	-114.12	53.88	701	-24.3	-22.3	-2	1
8387	1935-01-16	SION	ALTA	3015960	-114.12	53.88	701	-26	-23.4	-2.6	1
8388	1935-03-04	SION	ALTA	3015960	-114.12	53.88	701	-23.2	-21.4	-1.8	1
8389	1935-04-30	SION	ALTA	3015960	-114.12	53.88	701	0.8	1.3	-0.5	1
8390	1935-05-01	SION	ALTA	3015960	-114.12	53.88	701	-0.3	0.4	-0.7	1
8391	1935-05-02	SION	ALTA	3015960	-114.12	53.88	701	1.7	2.3	-0.6	1
8392	1935-12-27	SION	ALTA	3015960	-114.12	53.88	701	-12.3	-10.7	-1.6	1
8393	1935-12-30	SION	ALTA	3015960	-114.12	53.88	701	-12.3	-11.2	-1.1	1
8394	1935-12-31	SION	ALTA	3015960	-114.12	53.88	701	-12.9	-12.3	-0.6	1
8395	1936-02-10	SION	ALTA	3015960	-114.12	53.88	701	-23.8	-23.1	-0.7	1
8396	1936-10-31	SION	ALTA	3015960	-114.12	53.88	701	-10.6	-10	-0.6	1
8397	1936-12-01	SION	ALTA	3015960	-114.12	53.88	701	-10.6	-9.4	-1.2	1

8398	1936-12-02	SION	ALTA	3015960	-114.12	53.88	701	-13.3	-10.7	-2.6	1
8399	1936-12-04	SION	ALTA	3015960	-114.12	53.88	701	-21.5	-21.3	-0.2	1
8400	1936-12-12	SION	ALTA	3015960	-114.12	53.88	701	1	1.6	-0.6	1
8401	1937-01-12	SION	ALTA	3015960	-114.12	53.88	701	-11.9	-11.8	-0.1	1
8402	1937-04-01	SION	ALTA	3015960	-114.12	53.88	701	-0.3	0.8	-1.1	1
8403	1937-12-09	SION	ALTA	3015960	-114.12	53.88	701	-28.2	-26.4	-1.8	1
8404	1937-12-27	SION	ALTA	3015960	-114.12	53.88	701	-26.5	-24.9	-1.6	1
8405	1938-12-26	SION	ALTA	3015960	-114.12	53.88	701	-24.6	-24.3	-0.3	1
8406	1939-02-13	SION	ALTA	3015960	-114.12	53.88	701	-23.5	-22.7	-0.8	1
8407	1940-02-29	SION	ALTA	3015960	-114.12	53.88	701	-10.9	-10.4	-0.5	1
8408	1940-12-12	SION	ALTA	3015960	-114.12	53.88	701	-20.7	-18.9	-1.8	1
8409	1944-06-14	SION	ALTA	3015960	-114.12	53.88	701	7.4	7.8	-0.4	1
8410	1987-09-10	SION	ALTA	3015960	-114.12	53.88	701	2.3	6	-3.7	1
8411	1988-10-26	SION	ALTA	3015960	-114.12	53.88	701	-3	-2.5	-0.5	1
8412	1884-01-08	FORT CHIPEWYAN	ALTA	3072655	-111.12	58.77	238	-22.6	-22.2	-0.4	1
8413	1884-01-11	FORT CHIPEWYAN	ALTA	3072655	-111.12	58.77	238	-23.1	-22.2	-0.9	1
8414	1884-01-12	FORT CHIPEWYAN	ALTA	3072655	-111.12	58.77	238	-29.7	-28.3	-1.4	1
8415	1884-01-21	FORT CHIPEWYAN	ALTA	3072655	-111.12	58.77	238	-21.5	-21.1	-0.4	1
8416	1884-01-27	FORT CHIPEWYAN	ALTA	3072655	-111.12	58.77	238	-29.2	-27.8	-1.4	1
8417	1885-02-27	FORT CHIPEWYAN	ALTA	3072655	-111.12	58.77	238	-8.1	-7.8	-0.3	1
8418	1887-12-26	FORT CHIPEWYAN	ALTA	3072655	-111.12	58.77	238	-33.1	-32.8	-0.3	1
8419	1893-02-08	FORT CHIPEWYAN	ALTA	3072655	-111.12	58.77	238	-25.9	-15.6	-10.3	1
8420	1893-02-21	FORT CHIPEWYAN	ALTA	3072655	-111.12	58.77	238	-21	-15	-6	1
8421	1893-02-22	FORT CHIPEWYAN	ALTA	3072655	-111.12	58.77	238	-23.6	-15	-8.6	1
8422	1893-10-18	FORT CHIPEWYAN	ALTA	3072655	-111.12	58.77	238	4.4	5	-0.6	1
8423	1893-10-19	FORT CHIPEWYAN	ALTA	3072655	-111.12	58.77	238	-1.6	0	-1.6	1
8424	1893-11-19	FORT CHIPEWYAN	ALTA	3072655	-111.12	58.77	238	-11	-7.8	-3.2	1
8425	1893-11-20	FORT CHIPEWYAN	ALTA	3072655	-111.12	58.77	238	-18.4	-11.7	-6.7	1
8426	1893-11-22	FORT CHIPEWYAN	ALTA	3072655	-111.12	58.77	238	-25.3	-23.3	-2	1
8427	1893-11-23	FORT CHIPEWYAN	ALTA	3072655	-111.12	58.77	238	-26.4	-25.6	-0.8	1
8428	1894-09-22	FORT CHIPEWYAN	ALTA	3072655	-111.12	58.77	238	1.3	6.1	-4.8	1
8429	1895-01-07	FORT CHIPEWYAN	ALTA	3072655	-111.12	58.77	238	-41.4	-41.1	-0.3	1
8430	1895-01-14	FORT CHIPEWYAN	ALTA	3072655	-111.12	58.77	238	-17.4	-16.7	-0.7	1
8431	1897-02-23	FORT CHIPEWYAN	ALTA	3072655	-111.12	58.77	238	-29.2	-20	-9.2	1

8432	1899-01-26	FORT CHIPEWYAN	ALTA	3072655	-111.12	58.77	238	-32.5	-32.2	-0.3	1
8433	1899-03-17	FORT CHIPEWYAN	ALTA	3072655	-111.12	58.77	238	-22.6	-22.2	-0.4	1
8434	1907-03-13	FORT CHIPEWYAN	ALTA	3072655	-111.12	58.77	238	-14	-7.9	-6.1	1
8435	1909-12-15	FORT CHIPEWYAN	ALTA	3072655	-111.12	58.77	238	-12.9	-12.8	-0.1	1
8436	1909-12-23	FORT CHIPEWYAN	ALTA	3072655	-111.12	58.77	238	-17.8	-17.2	-0.6	1
8437	1909-12-30	FORT CHIPEWYAN	ALTA	3072655	-111.12	58.77	238	-16.3	-16.1	-0.2	1
8438	1910-01-25	FORT CHIPEWYAN	ALTA	3072655	-111.12	58.77	238	-14.6	-14.4	-0.2	1
8439	1912-01-15	FORT CHIPEWYAN	ALTA	3072655	-111.12	58.77	238	-30.9	-28.9	-2	1
8440	1934-01-14	FORT CHIPEWYAN	ALTA	3072655	-111.12	58.77	238	-29.7	-29.4	-0.3	1
8441	1934-10-25	FORT CHIPEWYAN	ALTA	3072655	-111.12	58.77	238	-4	-3.9	-0.1	1
8442	1935-04-12	FORT CHIPEWYAN	ALTA	3072655	-111.12	58.77	238	-8.1	-7.8	-0.3	1
8443	1938-12-26	FORT CHIPEWYAN	ALTA	3072655	-111.12	58.77	238	-32	-31.7	-0.3	1
8444	1944-10-31	FORT CHIPEWYAN	ALTA	3072655	-111.12	58.77	238	-9	-8.9	-0.1	1
8445	1944-12-26	FORT CHIPEWYAN	ALTA	3072655	-111.12	58.77	238	-18.4	-18.3	-0.1	1
8446	1946-01-24	FORT CHIPEWYAN	ALTA	3072655	-111.12	58.77	238	-29.5	-27.2	-2.3	1
8447	1946-03-27	FORT CHIPEWYAN	ALTA	3072655	-111.12	58.77	238	-4	-3.9	-0.1	1
8448	1946-03-30	FORT CHIPEWYAN	ALTA	3072655	-111.12	58.77	238	-0.3	0.6	-0.9	1
8449	1946-09-30	FORT CHIPEWYAN	ALTA	3072655	-111.12	58.77	238	6.5	7.2	-0.7	1
8450	1946-10-17	FORT CHIPEWYAN	ALTA	3072655	-111.12	58.77	238	0.4	0.6	-0.2	1
8451	1946-12-11	FORT CHIPEWYAN	ALTA	3072655	-111.12	58.77	238	-28.4	-27.8	-0.6	1
8452	1946-12-12	FORT CHIPEWYAN	ALTA	3072655	-111.12	58.77	238	-30.1	-30	-0.1	1
8453	1947-12-13	FORT CHIPEWYAN	ALTA	3072655	-111.12	58.77	238	-20.1	-18.9	-1.2	1
8454	1948-09-27	FORT CHIPEWYAN	ALTA	3072655	-111.12	58.77	238	10.7	11.1	-0.4	1
8455	1949-09-10	FORT CHIPEWYAN	ALTA	3072655	-111.12	58.77	238	-0.9	-0.6	-0.3	1
8456	1949-09-25	FORT CHIPEWYAN	ALTA	3072655	-111.12	58.77	238	5.1	5.6	-0.5	1
8457	1949-11-09	FORT CHIPEWYAN	ALTA	3072655	-111.12	58.77	238	-0.2	0	-0.2	1
8458	1949-11-11	FORT CHIPEWYAN	ALTA	3072655	-111.12	58.77	238	-2.1	-1.1	-1	1
8459	1950-09-29	FORT CHIPEWYAN	ALTA	3072655	-111.12	58.77	238	-0.2	0	-0.2	1
8460	1950-11-10	FORT CHIPEWYAN	ALTA	3072655	-111.12	58.77	238	-9.5	-9.4	-0.1	1
8461	1950-11-13	FORT CHIPEWYAN	ALTA	3072655	-111.12	58.77	238	-11.2	-8.3	-2.9	1
8462	1950-11-14	FORT CHIPEWYAN	ALTA	3072655	-111.12	58.77	238	-13.4	-11.1	-2.3	1
8463	1950-11-15	FORT CHIPEWYAN	ALTA	3072655	-111.12	58.77	238	-17.3	-13.9	-3.4	1
8464	1950-11-19	FORT CHIPEWYAN	ALTA	3072655	-111.12	58.77	238	-24.5	-22.8	-1.7	1
8465	1951-01-23	FORT CHIPEWYAN	ALTA	3072655	-111.12	58.77	238	-31.2	-30.6	-0.6	1

8466	1951-04-09	FORT CHIPEWYAN	ALTA	3072655	-111.12	58.77	238	-9	-8.9	-0.1	1
8467	1951-10-31	FORT CHIPEWYAN	ALTA	3072655	-111.12	58.77	238	-13.4	-13.3	-0.1	1
8468	1951-11-13	FORT CHIPEWYAN	ALTA	3072655	-111.12	58.77	238	-7.9	-6.7	-1.2	1
8469	1951-11-14	FORT CHIPEWYAN	ALTA	3072655	-111.12	58.77	238	-14	-10.6	-3.4	1
8470	1951-11-19	FORT CHIPEWYAN	ALTA	3072655	-111.12	58.77	238	-11.7	-9.4	-2.3	1
8471	1951-11-20	FORT CHIPEWYAN	ALTA	3072655	-111.12	58.77	238	-18.4	-12.8	-5.6	1
8472	1951-11-21	FORT CHIPEWYAN	ALTA	3072655	-111.12	58.77	238	-20.6	-18.3	-2.3	1
8473	1951-11-28	FORT CHIPEWYAN	ALTA	3072655	-111.12	58.77	238	-17.9	-17.8	-0.1	1
8474	1952-01-30	FORT CHIPEWYAN	ALTA	3072655	-111.12	58.77	238	-17.3	-17.2	-0.1	1
8475	1952-01-31	FORT CHIPEWYAN	ALTA	3072655	-111.12	58.77	238	-22.3	-22.2	-0.1	1
8476	1952-10-14	FORT CHIPEWYAN	ALTA	3072655	-111.12	58.77	238	-4	-3.3	-0.7	1
8477	1952-11-15	FORT CHIPEWYAN	ALTA	3072655	-111.12	58.77	238	-4.5	-3.9	-0.6	1
8478	1952-12-06	FORT CHIPEWYAN	ALTA	3072655	-111.12	58.77	238	-13.4	-13.3	-0.1	1
8479	1952-12-08	FORT CHIPEWYAN	ALTA	3072655	-111.12	58.77	238	-9.5	-9.4	-0.1	1
8480	1953-03-03	FORT CHIPEWYAN	ALTA	3072655	-111.12	58.77	238	-14.5	-13.9	-0.6	1
8481	1953-04-08	FORT CHIPEWYAN	ALTA	3072655	-111.12	58.77	238	-2.8	-2.2	-0.6	1
8482	1953-06-15	FORT CHIPEWYAN	ALTA	3072655	-111.12	58.77	238	4.6	5	-0.4	1
8483	1953-11-06	FORT CHIPEWYAN	ALTA	3072655	-111.12	58.77	238	-6.7	-5.6	-1.1	1
8484	1953-11-09	FORT CHIPEWYAN	ALTA	3072655	-111.12	58.77	238	-6.2	-5.6	-0.6	1
8485	1953-12-19	FORT CHIPEWYAN	ALTA	3072655	-111.12	58.77	238	-14.5	-14.4	-0.1	1
8486	1954-01-20	FORT CHIPEWYAN	ALTA	3072655	-111.12	58.77	238	-38.4	-38.3	-0.1	1
8487	1954-02-26	FORT CHIPEWYAN	ALTA	3072655	-111.12	58.77	238	-18.4	-18.3	-0.1	1
8488	1954-02-28	FORT CHIPEWYAN	ALTA	3072655	-111.12	58.77	238	-27.9	-27.2	-0.7	1
8489	1954-10-22	FORT CHIPEWYAN	ALTA	3072655	-111.12	58.77	238	0.4	0.6	-0.2	1
8490	1954-11-11	FORT CHIPEWYAN	ALTA	3072655	-111.12	58.77	238	-11.2	-11.1	-0.1	1
8491	1954-11-28	FORT CHIPEWYAN	ALTA	3072655	-111.12	58.77	238	-12.9	-12.2	-0.7	1
8492	1954-11-29	FORT CHIPEWYAN	ALTA	3072655	-111.12	58.77	238	-12.9	-12.8	-0.1	1
8493	1954-12-01	FORT CHIPEWYAN	ALTA	3072655	-111.12	58.77	238	-11.2	-11.1	-0.1	1
8494	1955-01-30	FORT CHIPEWYAN	ALTA	3072655	-111.12	58.77	238	-20.1	-19.4	-0.7	1
8495	1955-04-29	FORT CHIPEWYAN	ALTA	3072655	-111.12	58.77	238	-0.9	-0.6	-0.3	1
8496	1955-06-01	FORT CHIPEWYAN	ALTA	3072655	-111.12	58.77	238	7.1	7.8	-0.7	1
8497	1955-09-16	FORT CHIPEWYAN	ALTA	3072655	-111.12	58.77	238	8.8	9.4	-0.6	1
8498	1955-09-20	FORT CHIPEWYAN	ALTA	3072655	-111.12	58.77	238	4.6	5	-0.4	1
8499	1955-10-31	FORT CHIPEWYAN	ALTA	3072655	-111.12	58.77	238	-5.6	-5	-0.6	1

8500	1955-11-11	FORT CHIPEWYAN	ALTA	3072655	-111.12	58.77	238	-20.1	-20	-0.1	1
8501	1955-11-30	FORT CHIPEWYAN	ALTA	3072655	-111.12	58.77	238	-14.5	-14.4	-0.1	1
8502	1955-12-17	FORT CHIPEWYAN	ALTA	3072655	-111.12	58.77	238	-33.4	-33.3	-0.1	1
8503	1956-02-12	FORT CHIPEWYAN	ALTA	3072655	-111.12	58.77	238	-25.1	-25	-0.1	1
8504	1956-06-23	FORT CHIPEWYAN	ALTA	3072655	-111.12	58.77	238	13.1	13.3	-0.2	1
8505	1956-09-27	FORT CHIPEWYAN	ALTA	3072655	-111.12	58.77	238	-1.5	-1.1	-0.4	1
8506	1956-10-13	FORT CHIPEWYAN	ALTA	3072655	-111.12	58.77	238	-4.5	-4.4	-0.1	1
8507	1956-10-26	FORT CHIPEWYAN	ALTA	3072655	-111.12	58.77	238	-12.3	-11.1	-1.2	1
8508	1956-10-31	FORT CHIPEWYAN	ALTA	3072655	-111.12	58.77	238	-4.5	-4.4	-0.1	1
8509	1957-10-02	FORT CHIPEWYAN	ALTA	3072655	-111.12	58.77	238	-0.9	-0.6	-0.3	1
8510	1957-10-03	FORT CHIPEWYAN	ALTA	3072655	-111.12	58.77	238	-4	-3.3	-0.7	1
8511	1957-10-06	FORT CHIPEWYAN	ALTA	3072655	-111.12	58.77	238	-3.3	-2.8	-0.5	1
8512	1957-11-16	FORT CHIPEWYAN	ALTA	3072655	-111.12	58.77	238	-4.5	-4.4	-0.1	1
8513	1957-11-18	FORT CHIPEWYAN	ALTA	3072655	-111.12	58.77	238	-6.7	-6.1	-0.6	1
8514	1957-12-09	FORT CHIPEWYAN	ALTA	3072655	-111.12	58.77	238	-15.1	-15	-0.1	1
8515	1957-12-15	FORT CHIPEWYAN	ALTA	3072655	-111.12	58.77	238	-15.1	-15	-0.1	1
8516	1957-12-29	FORT CHIPEWYAN	ALTA	3072655	-111.12	58.77	238	-25.1	-25	-0.1	1
8517	1958-01-10	FORT CHIPEWYAN	ALTA	3072655	-111.12	58.77	238	-17.9	-17.8	-0.1	1
8518	1958-01-31	FORT CHIPEWYAN	ALTA	3072655	-111.12	58.77	238	-14.5	-14.4	-0.1	1
8519	1958-10-09	FORT CHIPEWYAN	ALTA	3072655	-111.12	58.77	238	-3.3	-2.8	-0.5	1
8520	1958-10-10	FORT CHIPEWYAN	ALTA	3072655	-111.12	58.77	238	-5.1	-4.4	-0.7	1
8521	1958-11-09	FORT CHIPEWYAN	ALTA	3072655	-111.12	58.77	238	-4	-3.9	-0.1	1
8522	1958-11-10	FORT CHIPEWYAN	ALTA	3072655	-111.12	58.77	238	-4	-2.8	-1.2	1
8523	1958-11-12	FORT CHIPEWYAN	ALTA	3072655	-111.12	58.77	238	-4.5	-2.8	-1.7	1
8524	1958-11-13	FORT CHIPEWYAN	ALTA	3072655	-111.12	58.77	238	-7.3	-6.1	-1.2	1
8525	1958-12-03	FORT CHIPEWYAN	ALTA	3072655	-111.12	58.77	238	-17.9	-17.8	-0.1	1
8526	1958-12-04	FORT CHIPEWYAN	ALTA	3072655	-111.12	58.77	238	-22.3	-21.7	-0.6	1
8527	1958-12-17	FORT CHIPEWYAN	ALTA	3072655	-111.12	58.77	238	-22.9	-21.7	-1.2	1
8528	1958-12-22	FORT CHIPEWYAN	ALTA	3072655	-111.12	58.77	238	-14	-13.3	-0.7	1
8529	1959-01-02	FORT CHIPEWYAN	ALTA	3072655	-111.12	58.77	238	-34	-32.8	-1.2	1
8530	1959-01-03	FORT CHIPEWYAN	ALTA	3072655	-111.12	58.77	238	-32.3	-31.1	-1.2	1
8531	1959-01-04	FORT CHIPEWYAN	ALTA	3072655	-111.12	58.77	238	-34	-32.8	-1.2	1
8532	1959-01-09	FORT CHIPEWYAN	ALTA	3072655	-111.12	58.77	238	-19	-18.9	-0.1	1
8533	1959-04-30	FORT CHIPEWYAN	ALTA	3072655	-111.12	58.77	238	-4.5	-3.9	-0.6	1

8534	1959-09-28	FORT CHIPEWYAN	ALTA	3072655	-111.12	58.77	238	-2.1	-1.7	-0.4	1
8535	1959-10-04	FORT CHIPEWYAN	ALTA	3072655	-111.12	58.77	238	-4.5	-4.4	-0.1	1
8536	1959-10-12	FORT CHIPEWYAN	ALTA	3072655	-111.12	58.77	238	-4	-3.9	-0.1	1
8537	1959-10-27	FORT CHIPEWYAN	ALTA	3072655	-111.12	58.77	238	-2.8	-2.2	-0.6	1
8538	1959-11-02	FORT CHIPEWYAN	ALTA	3072655	-111.12	58.77	238	-7.9	-7.2	-0.7	1
8539	1959-11-03	FORT CHIPEWYAN	ALTA	3072655	-111.12	58.77	238	-11.2	-11.1	-0.1	1
8540	1959-11-10	FORT CHIPEWYAN	ALTA	3072655	-111.12	58.77	238	-14	-13.3	-0.7	1
8541	1959-11-11	FORT CHIPEWYAN	ALTA	3072655	-111.12	58.77	238	-17.9	-17.2	-0.7	1
8542	1959-11-12	FORT CHIPEWYAN	ALTA	3072655	-111.12	58.77	238	-21.2	-21.1	-0.1	1
8543	1960-10-13	FORT CHIPEWYAN	ALTA	3072655	-111.12	58.77	238	-0.2	0	-0.2	1
8544	1960-10-21	FORT CHIPEWYAN	ALTA	3072655	-111.12	58.77	238	-5.1	-5	-0.1	1
8545	1960-11-02	FORT CHIPEWYAN	ALTA	3072655	-111.12	58.77	238	-3.3	-2.2	-1.1	1
8546	1960-11-15	FORT CHIPEWYAN	ALTA	3072655	-111.12	58.77	238	-8.4	-8.3	-0.1	1
8547	1960-12-10	FORT CHIPEWYAN	ALTA	3072655	-111.12	58.77	238	-7.3	-7.2	-0.1	1
8548	1960-12-19	FORT CHIPEWYAN	ALTA	3072655	-111.12	58.77	238	-29.5	-29.4	-0.1	1
8549	1961-01-16	FORT CHIPEWYAN	ALTA	3072655	-111.12	58.77	238	-19	-18.9	-0.1	1
8550	1961-02-15	FORT CHIPEWYAN	ALTA	3072655	-111.12	58.77	238	-25.6	-25	-0.6	1
8551	1961-11-22	FORT CHIPEWYAN	ALTA	3072655	-111.12	58.77	238	-11.2	-10.6	-0.6	1
8552	1967-11-09	FORT CHIPEWYAN	ALTA	3072655	-111.12	58.77	238	-5.6	-5	-0.6	1
8553	1967-11-11	FORT CHIPEWYAN	ALTA	3072655	-111.12	58.77	238	-9	-8.8	-0.2	1
8554	1994-06-09	SHEPHERD BAY	NU	2303685	-93.43	68.82	43	0.4	0.9	-0.5	1
8555	2010-04-20	SHEPHERD BAY	NU	2303685	-93.43	68.82	43	-11	-10.9	-0.1	1
8556	1928-04-29	CORONATION	ALTA	3011887	-111.45	52.08	791	-0.1	0.4	-0.5	1
8557	1928-07-04	CORONATION	ALTA	3011887	-111.45	52.08	791	9.4	10.4	-1	1
8558	1929-05-24	CORONATION	ALTA	3011887	-111.45	52.08	791	6.5	7	-0.5	1
8559	1929-06-16	CORONATION	ALTA	3011887	-111.45	52.08	791	9.1	9.6	-0.5	1
8560	1934-08-30	CORONATION	ALTA	3011887	-111.45	52.08	791	5.5	5.6	-0.1	1
8561	1936-06-16	CORONATION	ALTA	3011887	-111.45	52.08	791	8.5	8.9	-0.4	1
8562	1936-09-12	CORONATION	ALTA	3011887	-111.45	52.08	791	2.2	2.4	-0.2	1
8563	1936-10-31	CORONATION	ALTA	3011887	-111.45	52.08	791	-0.8	-0.3	-0.5	1
8564	1940-04-22	CORONATION	ALTA	3011887	-111.45	52.08	791	0.3	0.4	-0.1	1
8565	1940-09-07	CORONATION	ALTA	3011887	-111.45	52.08	791	8.6	8.7	-0.1	1
8566	1941-06-06	CORONATION	ALTA	3011887	-111.45	52.08	791	8	8.3	-0.3	1
8567	2009-04-22	HIGH RIVER	ALTA	3033250	-114.17	50.48	1580	4.2	9.8	-5.6	1

8568	1991-02-05	KINDERSLEY	SASK	4043901	-109.18	51.52	694	2	3.5	-1.5	1
8569	1929-09-18	DONNACONA	QUE	7011982	-71.73	46.68	15	12.7	12.8	-0.1	1
8570	1930-11-17	DONNACONA	QUE	7011982	-71.73	46.68	15	4	4.1	-0.1	1
8571	1939-12-08	DONNACONA	QUE	7011982	-71.73	46.68	15	-5.1	-4.7	-0.4	1
8572	1941-12-07	DONNACONA	QUE	7011982	-71.73	46.68	15	-6.3	-6	-0.3	1
8573	1989-12-26	DONNACONA	QUE	7011982	-71.73	46.68	15	-21	-8	-13	1
8574	1949-11-18	ST ANTHONY	NFLD	8403389	-55.6	51.37	33	-0.5	-0.2	-0.3	1
8575	1951-03-29	ST ANTHONY	NFLD	8403389	-55.6	51.37	33	-0.5	-0.3	-0.2	1
8576	1951-04-10	ST ANTHONY	NFLD	8403389	-55.6	51.37	33	-0.5	-0.2	-0.3	1
8577	1951-04-13	ST ANTHONY	NFLD	8403389	-55.6	51.37	33	-0.4	-0.2	-0.2	1
8578	1951-05-25	ST ANTHONY	NFLD	8403389	-55.6	51.37	33	-0.5	0.3	-0.8	1
8579	1952-12-18	ST ANTHONY	NFLD	8403389	-55.6	51.37	33	-8.7	-8.5	-0.2	1
8580	1954-02-26	ST ANTHONY	NFLD	8403389	-55.6	51.37	33	-0.4	0.3	-0.7	1
8581	1954-02-28	ST ANTHONY	NFLD	8403389	-55.6	51.37	33	-0.4	-0.3	-0.1	1
8582	1954-05-06	ST ANTHONY	NFLD	8403389	-55.6	51.37	33	0.2	0.4	-0.2	1
8583	1955-01-09	ST ANTHONY	NFLD	8403389	-55.6	51.37	33	0.4	0.7	-0.3	1
8584	1956-01-08	ST ANTHONY	NFLD	8403389	-55.6	51.37	33	-1	-0.2	-0.8	1
8585	1956-01-16	ST ANTHONY	NFLD	8403389	-55.6	51.37	33	-0.5	-0.2	-0.3	1
8586	1956-01-17	ST ANTHONY	NFLD	8403389	-55.6	51.37	33	-1	-0.2	-0.8	1
8587	1956-01-18	ST ANTHONY	NFLD	8403389	-55.6	51.37	33	-1	-0.2	-0.8	1
8588	1956-01-22	ST ANTHONY	NFLD	8403389	-55.6	51.37	33	-0.5	0.3	-0.8	1
8589	1956-01-23	ST ANTHONY	NFLD	8403389	-55.6	51.37	33	-0.5	-0.2	-0.3	1
8590	1956-01-24	ST ANTHONY	NFLD	8403389	-55.6	51.37	33	-0.5	-0.2	-0.3	1
8591	1956-04-09	ST ANTHONY	NFLD	8403389	-55.6	51.37	33	-0.4	0.3	-0.7	1
8592	1956-04-10	ST ANTHONY	NFLD	8403389	-55.6	51.37	33	-0.4	-0.2	-0.2	1
8593	1957-03-12	ST ANTHONY	NFLD	8403389	-55.6	51.37	33	-0.5	-0.3	-0.2	1
8594	1957-03-23	ST ANTHONY	NFLD	8403389	-55.6	51.37	33	-0.5	-0.3	-0.2	1
8595	1957-12-30	ST ANTHONY	NFLD	8403389	-55.6	51.37	33	-0.5	-0.3	-0.2	1
8596	1958-01-19	ST ANTHONY	NFLD	8403389	-55.6	51.37	33	0.3	0.4	-0.1	1
8597	1958-02-03	ST ANTHONY	NFLD	8403389	-55.6	51.37	33	-0.9	-0.3	-0.6	1
8598	1958-02-16	ST ANTHONY	NFLD	8403389	-55.6	51.37	33	-0.5	-0.3	-0.2	1
8599	1960-01-19	ST ANTHONY	NFLD	8403389	-55.6	51.37	33	-0.5	-0.2	-0.3	1
8600	1960-02-09	ST ANTHONY	NFLD	8403389	-55.6	51.37	33	-0.5	-0.2	-0.3	1
8601	1960-02-10	ST ANTHONY	NFLD	8403389	-55.6	51.37	33	-0.5	-0.2	-0.3	1

8602	1960-02-13	ST ANTHONY	NFLD	8403389	-55.6	51.37	33	-0.5	0.2	-0.7	1
8603	1960-03-01	ST ANTHONY	NFLD	8403389	-55.6	51.37	33	-1.3	-1	-0.3	1
8604	1960-11-24	ST ANTHONY	NFLD	8403389	-55.6	51.37	33	-0.5	-0.2	-0.3	1
8605	1960-11-26	ST ANTHONY	NFLD	8403389	-55.6	51.37	33	-0.5	-0.3	-0.2	1
8606	1960-12-07	ST ANTHONY	NFLD	8403389	-55.6	51.37	33	-0.5	0.2	-0.7	1
8607	1961-04-06	ST ANTHONY	NFLD	8403389	-55.6	51.37	33	0.2	0.3	-0.1	1
8608	1961-11-11	ST ANTHONY	NFLD	8403389	-55.6	51.37	33	-0.5	-0.2	-0.3	1
8609	1964-02-20	ST ANTHONY	NFLD	8403389	-55.6	51.37	33	-0.4	-0.2	-0.2	1
8610	1964-11-14	ST ANTHONY	NFLD	8403389	-55.6	51.37	33	-0.5	-0.2	-0.3	1
8611	1964-11-15	ST ANTHONY	NFLD	8403389	-55.6	51.37	33	-0.5	-0.2	-0.3	1
8612	1965-03-11	ST ANTHONY	NFLD	8403389	-55.6	51.37	33	-0.5	-0.2	-0.3	1
8613	1966-01-24	ST ANTHONY	NFLD	8403389	-55.6	51.37	33	-1.7	-1.6	-0.1	1
8614	1967-01-05	ST ANTHONY	NFLD	8403389	-55.6	51.37	33	-1.6	-0.9	-0.7	1
8615	1969-01-10	ST ANTHONY	NFLD	8403389	-55.6	51.37	33	-0.1	0.5	-0.6	1
8616	1969-01-11	ST ANTHONY	NFLD	8403389	-55.6	51.37	33	-0.2	0.5	-0.7	1
8617	1969-01-12	ST ANTHONY	NFLD	8403389	-55.6	51.37	33	-0.8	-0.3	-0.5	1
8618	1969-03-11	ST ANTHONY	NFLD	8403389	-55.6	51.37	33	-0.2	0.5	-0.7	1
8619	1970-04-10	ST ANTHONY	NFLD	8403389	-55.6	51.37	33	0	0.5	-0.5	1
8620	1970-04-11	ST ANTHONY	NFLD	8403389	-55.6	51.37	33	-0.1	0.5	-0.6	1
8621	1970-08-31	ST ANTHONY	NFLD	8403389	-55.6	51.37	33	8.7	8.9	-0.2	1
8622	1983-08-18	ST ANTHONY	NFLD	8403389	-55.6	51.37	33	6.3	6.9	-0.6	1
8623	1985-08-28	ST ANTHONY	NFLD	8403389	-55.6	51.37	33	9.4	9.6	-0.2	1
8624	1986-10-30	ST ANTHONY	NFLD	8403389	-55.6	51.37	33	4.1	4.7	-0.6	1
8625	1987-03-18	ST ANTHONY	NFLD	8403389	-55.6	51.37	33	-0.2	0	-0.2	1
8626	1990-11-27	ST ANTHONY	NFLD	8403389	-55.6	51.37	33	-1.3	-0.6	-0.7	1
8627	2015-01-19	AROOSTOOK	NB	8100300	-67.72	46.8	80	2	5	-3	1
8628	2016-12-24	AROOSTOOK	NB	8100300	-67.72	46.8	80	-16	-15	-1	1
8629	1908-09-30	FORT VERMILION	ALTA	3072723	-116.03	58.38	289	3.3	3.6	-0.3	1
8630	1909-01-11	FORT VERMILION	ALTA	3072723	-116.03	58.38	289	-22.8	-20.7	-2.1	1
8631	1909-02-15	FORT VERMILION	ALTA	3072723	-116.03	58.38	289	-22.8	-20.8	-2	1
8632	1910-01-02	FORT VERMILION	ALTA	3072723	-116.03	58.38	289	-26.1	-23.1	-3	1
8633	1910-01-08	FORT VERMILION	ALTA	3072723	-116.03	58.38	289	-21.7	-21.6	-0.1	1
8634	1910-01-12	FORT VERMILION	ALTA	3072723	-116.03	58.38	289	-21.7	-21.1	-0.6	1
8635	1910-04-14	FORT VERMILION	ALTA	3072723	-116.03	58.38	289	1.1	2	-0.9	1

8636	1910-05-27	FORT VERMILION	ALTA	3072723	-116.03	58.38	289	4.4	5.3	-0.9	1
8637	1910-05-28	FORT VERMILION	ALTA	3072723	-116.03	58.38	289	5	5.3	-0.3	1
8638	1910-11-05	FORT VERMILION	ALTA	3072723	-116.03	58.38	289	-12.2	-11.1	-1.1	1
8639	1911-01-03	FORT VERMILION	ALTA	3072723	-116.03	58.38	289	-21.7	-20.3	-1.4	1
8640	1911-01-07	FORT VERMILION	ALTA	3072723	-116.03	58.38	289	-23.9	-23.1	-0.8	1
8641	1911-01-11	FORT VERMILION	ALTA	3072723	-116.03	58.38	289	-59.4	-59.2	-0.2	1
8642	1911-03-01	FORT VERMILION	ALTA	3072723	-116.03	58.38	289	6.1	7.7	-1.6	1
8643	1911-03-10	FORT VERMILION	ALTA	3072723	-116.03	58.38	289	-24.4	-24.2	-0.2	1
8644	1911-12-06	FORT VERMILION	ALTA	3072723	-116.03	58.38	289	-11.1	-10	-1.1	1
8645	1912-01-13	FORT VERMILION	ALTA	3072723	-116.03	58.38	289	-30	-27.4	-2.6	1
8646	1912-11-10	FORT VERMILION	ALTA	3072723	-116.03	58.38	289	-8.9	-8.4	-0.5	1
8647	1914-01-30	FORT VERMILION	ALTA	3072723	-116.03	58.38	289	-22.2	-20.7	-1.5	1
8648	1914-02-11	FORT VERMILION	ALTA	3072723	-116.03	58.38	289	-23.9	-23.1	-0.8	1
8649	1914-11-22	FORT VERMILION	ALTA	3072723	-116.03	58.38	289	-1.1	-1	-0.1	1
8650	1914-12-09	FORT VERMILION	ALTA	3072723	-116.03	58.38	289	-15.6	-15.1	-0.5	1
8651	1915-11-11	FORT VERMILION	ALTA	3072723	-116.03	58.38	289	-15	-14.6	-0.4	1
8652	1917-01-11	FORT VERMILION	ALTA	3072723	-116.03	58.38	289	-25.6	-22.7	-2.9	1
8653	1917-12-28	FORT VERMILION	ALTA	3072723	-116.03	58.38	289	-52.2	-51.3	-0.9	1
8654	1919-12-25	FORT VERMILION	ALTA	3072723	-116.03	58.38	289	-24.4	-22.1	-2.3	1
8655	1921-11-27	FORT VERMILION	ALTA	3072723	-116.03	58.38	289	-19.4	-17.9	-1.5	1
8656	1921-12-06	FORT VERMILION	ALTA	3072723	-116.03	58.38	289	-12.2	-10	-2.2	1
8657	1922-02-08	FORT VERMILION	ALTA	3072723	-116.03	58.38	289	-26.7	-24.9	-1.8	1
8658	1922-06-06	FORT VERMILION	ALTA	3072723	-116.03	58.38	289	4.4	4.7	-0.3	1
8659	1922-09-29	FORT VERMILION	ALTA	3072723	-116.03	58.38	289	4.4	4.6	-0.2	1
8660	1922-10-28	FORT VERMILION	ALTA	3072723	-116.03	58.38	289	-1.7	-1.1	-0.6	1
8661	1923-07-28	GRANDE PRAIRIE	ALTA	3072921	-118.88	55.18	669	10.4	10.6	-0.2	1
8662	1930-11-12	GRANDE PRAIRIE	ALTA	3072921	-118.88	55.18	669	-12.9	-10	-2.9	1
8663	1930-11-23	GRANDE PRAIRIE	ALTA	3072921	-118.88	55.18	669	-0.1	1.7	-1.8	1
8664	1930-12-08	GRANDE PRAIRIE	ALTA	3072921	-118.88	55.18	669	1.3	1.7	-0.4	1
8665	1931-01-19	GRANDE PRAIRIE	ALTA	3072921	-118.88	55.18	669	-15.4	-3.9	-11.5	1
8666	1932-03-17	GRANDE PRAIRIE	ALTA	3072921	-118.88	55.18	669	-11.3	-11.1	-0.2	1
8667	1932-04-21	GRANDE PRAIRIE	ALTA	3072921	-118.88	55.18	669	-7.1	-6.7	-0.4	1
8668	1933-02-13	GRANDE PRAIRIE	ALTA	3072921	-118.88	55.18	669	-10.1	-9.4	-0.7	1
8669	1917-06-14	HORNEPAYNE	ONT	6053575	-84.77	49.2	335	5	5.4	-0.4	1

8670	1917-10-14	HORNEPAYNE	ONT	6053575	-84.77	49.2	335	1.7	2.5	-0.8	1
8671	1917-10-19	HORNEPAYNE	ONT	6053575	-84.77	49.2	335	-1.1	-0.3	-0.8	1
8672	1917-12-09	HORNEPAYNE	ONT	6053575	-84.77	49.2	335	-23.9	-23.8	-0.1	1
8673	1917-12-10	HORNEPAYNE	ONT	6053575	-84.77	49.2	335	-26.1	-25.5	-0.6	1
8674	1918-03-09	HORNEPAYNE	ONT	6053575	-84.77	49.2	335	-23.3	-22.8	-0.5	1
8675	1918-11-28	HORNEPAYNE	ONT	6053575	-84.77	49.2	335	-1.1	-1	-0.1	1
8676	1919-03-26	HORNEPAYNE	ONT	6053575	-84.77	49.2	335	1.7	3.4	-1.7	1
8677	1919-06-06	HORNEPAYNE	ONT	6053575	-84.77	49.2	335	-1.1	0.5	-1.6	1
8678	1919-10-21	HORNEPAYNE	ONT	6053575	-84.77	49.2	335	4.4	5.4	-1	1
8679	1919-11-25	HORNEPAYNE	ONT	6053575	-84.77	49.2	335	-23.3	-22.9	-0.4	1
8680	1920-05-13	HORNEPAYNE	ONT	6053575	-84.77	49.2	335	2.2	3.8	-1.6	1
8681	1921-03-14	HORNEPAYNE	ONT	6053575	-84.77	49.2	335	-5.6	-5.5	-0.1	1
8682	1921-06-22	HORNEPAYNE	ONT	6053575	-84.77	49.2	335	29.4	30.3	-0.9	1
8683	1922-11-10	HORNEPAYNE	ONT	6053575	-84.77	49.2	335	1.7	1.9	-0.2	1
8684	1927-05-09	HORNEPAYNE	ONT	6053575	-84.77	49.2	335	1.7	1.9	-0.2	1
8685	1927-05-10	HORNEPAYNE	ONT	6053575	-84.77	49.2	335	1.1	1.9	-0.8	1
8686	1929-03-13	HORNEPAYNE	ONT	6053575	-84.77	49.2	335	-2.2	-1	-1.2	1
8687	1929-03-14	HORNEPAYNE	ONT	6053575	-84.77	49.2	335	4.4	4.8	-0.4	1
8688	1929-03-23	HORNEPAYNE	ONT	6053575	-84.77	49.2	335	1.7	1.9	-0.2	1
8689	1929-03-25	HORNEPAYNE	ONT	6053575	-84.77	49.2	335	2.8	3.4	-0.6	1
8690	1929-05-15	HORNEPAYNE	ONT	6053575	-84.77	49.2	335	-6.7	-6.2	-0.5	1
8691	1929-06-11	HORNEPAYNE	ONT	6053575	-84.77	49.2	335	5	5.9	-0.9	1
8692	1929-08-14	HORNEPAYNE	ONT	6053575	-84.77	49.2	335	6.7	7.2	-0.5	1
8693	1929-09-03	HORNEPAYNE	ONT	6053575	-84.77	49.2	335	10.6	10.7	-0.1	1
8694	1929-10-12	HORNEPAYNE	ONT	6053575	-84.77	49.2	335	7.8	8.4	-0.6	1
8695	1929-10-19	HORNEPAYNE	ONT	6053575	-84.77	49.2	335	2.8	2.9	-0.1	1
8696	1929-10-20	HORNEPAYNE	ONT	6053575	-84.77	49.2	335	2.2	2.5	-0.3	1
8697	1929-10-21	HORNEPAYNE	ONT	6053575	-84.77	49.2	335	0.6	1.9	-1.3	1
8698	1929-10-26	HORNEPAYNE	ONT	6053575	-84.77	49.2	335	3.3	3.4	-0.1	1
8699	1929-10-27	HORNEPAYNE	ONT	6053575	-84.77	49.2	335	-5	-4.2	-0.8	1
8700	1929-11-11	HORNEPAYNE	ONT	6053575	-84.77	49.2	335	-1.1	0.7	-1.8	1
8701	1930-01-02	HORNEPAYNE	ONT	6053575	-84.77	49.2	335	-6.7	-6.3	-0.4	1
8702	1930-01-03	HORNEPAYNE	ONT	6053575	-84.77	49.2	335	-20.6	-20.5	-0.1	1
8703	1930-01-07	HORNEPAYNE	ONT	6053575	-84.77	49.2	335	-22.2	-21.4	-0.8	1

8704	1930-02-04	HORNEPAYNE	ONT	6053575	-84.77	49.2	335	-18.9	-18.8	-0.1	1
8705	1930-02-13	HORNEPAYNE	ONT	6053575	-84.77	49.2	335	-23.3	-22.9	-0.4	1
8706	1930-02-23	HORNEPAYNE	ONT	6053575	-84.77	49.2	335	1.7	2.5	-0.8	1
8707	1930-03-01	HORNEPAYNE	ONT	6053575	-84.77	49.2	335	-9.4	-9.3	-0.1	1
8708	1930-03-11	HORNEPAYNE	ONT	6053575	-84.77	49.2	335	-3.9	-3	-0.9	1
8709	1930-04-13	HORNEPAYNE	ONT	6053575	-84.77	49.2	335	0	0.4	-0.4	1
8710	1930-11-12	HORNEPAYNE	ONT	6053575	-84.77	49.2	335	7.2	8.8	-1.6	1
8711	1930-11-20	HORNEPAYNE	ONT	6053575	-84.77	49.2	335	1.7	2.9	-1.2	1
8712	1930-11-21	HORNEPAYNE	ONT	6053575	-84.77	49.2	335	1.7	2.5	-0.8	1
8713	1930-11-22	HORNEPAYNE	ONT	6053575	-84.77	49.2	335	-3.9	-3.6	-0.3	1
8714	1930-12-14	HORNEPAYNE	ONT	6053575	-84.77	49.2	335	-22.2	-20.7	-1.5	1
8715	1931-01-28	HORNEPAYNE	ONT	6053575	-84.77	49.2	335	-18.9	-18.8	-0.1	1
8716	1931-02-04	HORNEPAYNE	ONT	6053575	-84.77	49.2	335	-23.3	-22.9	-0.4	1
8717	1931-04-21	HORNEPAYNE	ONT	6053575	-84.77	49.2	335	-4.4	-3.6	-0.8	1
8718	1931-05-02	HORNEPAYNE	ONT	6053575	-84.77	49.2	335	2.2	3.5	-1.3	1
8719	1931-05-20	HORNEPAYNE	ONT	6053575	-84.77	49.2	335	-0.6	1.3	-1.9	1
8720	1931-05-22	HORNEPAYNE	ONT	6053575	-84.77	49.2	335	1.1	1.9	-0.8	1
8721	1931-10-07	HORNEPAYNE	ONT	6053575	-84.77	49.2	335	1.7	3.4	-1.7	1
8722	1931-10-11	HORNEPAYNE	ONT	6053575	-84.77	49.2	335	1.7	3.5	-1.8	1
8723	1931-10-16	HORNEPAYNE	ONT	6053575	-84.77	49.2	335	3.3	3.5	-0.2	1
8724	1931-10-17	HORNEPAYNE	ONT	6053575	-84.77	49.2	335	1.7	1.9	-0.2	1
8725	1931-10-29	HORNEPAYNE	ONT	6053575	-84.77	49.2	335	4.4	5.9	-1.5	1
8726	1931-12-17	HORNEPAYNE	ONT	6053575	-84.77	49.2	335	-15.6	-15.1	-0.5	1
8727	1932-02-08	HORNEPAYNE	ONT	6053575	-84.77	49.2	335	-26.1	-22.9	-3.2	1
8728	1932-02-12	HORNEPAYNE	ONT	6053575	-84.77	49.2	335	-16.7	-16.1	-0.6	1
8729	1932-03-11	HORNEPAYNE	ONT	6053575	-84.77	49.2	335	-22.2	-21.4	-0.8	1
8730	1932-04-07	HORNEPAYNE	ONT	6053575	-84.77	49.2	335	1.1	1.2	-0.1	1
8731	1932-08-24	HORNEPAYNE	ONT	6053575	-84.77	49.2	335	13.9	14.2	-0.3	1
8732	1932-09-28	HORNEPAYNE	ONT	6053575	-84.77	49.2	335	9.4	10.3	-0.9	1
8733	1932-10-02	HORNEPAYNE	ONT	6053575	-84.77	49.2	335	9.4	10.4	-1	1
8734	1932-10-04	HORNEPAYNE	ONT	6053575	-84.77	49.2	335	2.8	3.4	-0.6	1
8735	1932-10-05	HORNEPAYNE	ONT	6053575	-84.77	49.2	335	1.7	2.5	-0.8	1
8736	1932-10-20	HORNEPAYNE	ONT	6053575	-84.77	49.2	335	4.4	5.9	-1.5	1
8737	1932-10-25	HORNEPAYNE	ONT	6053575	-84.77	49.2	335	4.4	6	-1.6	1

8738	1932-10-29	HORNEPAYNE	ONT	6053575	-84.77	49.2	335	-3.9	-3	-0.9	1
8739	1932-11-07	HORNEPAYNE	ONT	6053575	-84.77	49.2	335	-6.7	-6.3	-0.4	1
8740	1932-11-09	HORNEPAYNE	ONT	6053575	-84.77	49.2	335	0	0.5	-0.5	1
8741	1932-11-10	HORNEPAYNE	ONT	6053575	-84.77	49.2	335	-0.6	1.2	-1.8	1
8742	1932-11-11	HORNEPAYNE	ONT	6053575	-84.77	49.2	335	-3.9	-3	-0.9	1
8743	1932-11-12	HORNEPAYNE	ONT	6053575	-84.77	49.2	335	-3.9	-3	-0.9	1
8744	1932-12-01	HORNEPAYNE	ONT	6053575	-84.77	49.2	335	1.7	3.4	-1.7	1
8745	1932-12-22	HORNEPAYNE	ONT	6053575	-84.77	49.2	335	-2.8	-1.7	-1.1	1
8746	1932-12-28	HORNEPAYNE	ONT	6053575	-84.77	49.2	335	-3.9	-3	-0.9	1
8747	1933-01-11	HORNEPAYNE	ONT	6053575	-84.77	49.2	335	-24.4	-22.8	-1.6	1
8748	1933-01-20	HORNEPAYNE	ONT	6053575	-84.77	49.2	335	-16.7	-16	-0.7	1
8749	1933-04-24	HORNEPAYNE	ONT	6053575	-84.77	49.2	335	0	0.7	-0.7	1
8750	1933-05-01	HORNEPAYNE	ONT	6053575	-84.77	49.2	335	3.3	3.8	-0.5	1
8751	1933-06-07	HORNEPAYNE	ONT	6053575	-84.77	49.2	335	14.4	14.8	-0.4	1
8752	1933-10-08	HORNEPAYNE	ONT	6053575	-84.77	49.2	335	2.2	2.9	-0.7	1
8753	1933-10-17	HORNEPAYNE	ONT	6053575	-84.77	49.2	335	-3.3	-3	-0.3	1
8754	1933-11-13	HORNEPAYNE	ONT	6053575	-84.77	49.2	335	-22.2	-20.5	-1.7	1
8755	1933-11-14	HORNEPAYNE	ONT	6053575	-84.77	49.2	335	-23.3	-21.4	-1.9	1
8756	1933-11-16	HORNEPAYNE	ONT	6053575	-84.77	49.2	335	-21.1	-20	-1.1	1
8757	1933-11-18	HORNEPAYNE	ONT	6053575	-84.77	49.2	335	-22.2	-20.5	-1.7	1
8758	1934-05-05	HORNEPAYNE	ONT	6053575	-84.77	49.2	335	3.3	3.8	-0.5	1
8759	1934-09-27	HORNEPAYNE	ONT	6053575	-84.77	49.2	335	2.2	2.9	-0.7	1
8760	1935-12-20	HORNEPAYNE	ONT	6053575	-84.77	49.2	335	-28.9	-28	-0.9	1
8761	1936-03-10	HORNEPAYNE	ONT	6053575	-84.77	49.2	335	2.2	2.5	-0.3	1
8762	1936-04-16	HORNEPAYNE	ONT	6053575	-84.77	49.2	335	1.1	1.9	-0.8	1
8763	1936-09-26	HORNEPAYNE	ONT	6053575	-84.77	49.2	335	4.4	5.9	-1.5	1
8764	1936-09-27	HORNEPAYNE	ONT	6053575	-84.77	49.2	335	2.2	2.5	-0.3	1
8765	1936-12-07	HORNEPAYNE	ONT	6053575	-84.77	49.2	335	-26.7	-26.1	-0.6	1
8766	1937-02-21	HORNEPAYNE	ONT	6053575	-84.77	49.2	335	4.4	4.8	-0.4	1
8767	1937-02-22	HORNEPAYNE	ONT	6053575	-84.77	49.2	335	4.4	4.8	-0.4	1
8768	1937-04-19	HORNEPAYNE	ONT	6053575	-84.77	49.2	335	1.1	2.5	-1.4	1
8769	1937-10-07	HORNEPAYNE	ONT	6053575	-84.77	49.2	335	0	0.5	-0.5	1
8770	1938-02-14	HORNEPAYNE	ONT	6053575	-84.77	49.2	335	-22.2	-21.4	-0.8	1
8771	1938-10-03	HORNEPAYNE	ONT	6053575	-84.77	49.2	335	0.6	1.3	-0.7	1

8772	1938-10-04	HORNEPAYNE	ONT	6053575	-84.77	49.2	335	1.7	2.5	-0.8	1
8773	1938-12-27	HORNEPAYNE	ONT	6053575	-84.77	49.2	335	-24.4	-23.9	-0.5	1
8774	1940-05-15	HORNEPAYNE	ONT	6053575	-84.77	49.2	335	0	0.5	-0.5	1
8775	1941-05-08	HORNEPAYNE	ONT	6053575	-84.77	49.2	335	1.1	2.5	-1.4	1
8776	1941-10-31	HORNEPAYNE	ONT	6053575	-84.77	49.2	335	-0.6	0.6	-1.2	1
8777	1941-11-08	HORNEPAYNE	ONT	6053575	-84.77	49.2	335	-2.8	-2.3	-0.5	1
8778	1942-11-01	HORNEPAYNE	ONT	6053575	-84.77	49.2	335	-1.1	-1	-0.1	1
8779	1946-01-05	HORNEPAYNE	ONT	6053575	-84.77	49.2	335	1.7	3.4	-1.7	1
8780	1946-01-06	HORNEPAYNE	ONT	6053575	-84.77	49.2	335	1.1	1.9	-0.8	1
8781	1946-02-16	HORNEPAYNE	ONT	6053575	-84.77	49.2	335	-26.1	-25.5	-0.6	1
8782	1948-03-21	HORNEPAYNE	ONT	6053575	-84.77	49.2	335	0	1.2	-1.2	1
8783	1948-03-29	HORNEPAYNE	ONT	6053575	-84.77	49.2	335	-4.4	-3.6	-0.8	1
8784	1948-04-01	HORNEPAYNE	ONT	6053575	-84.77	49.2	335	-1.7	-1	-0.7	1
8785	1948-05-06	HORNEPAYNE	ONT	6053575	-84.77	49.2	335	2.2	2.5	-0.3	1
8786	1948-05-27	HORNEPAYNE	ONT	6053575	-84.77	49.2	335	6.7	7.2	-0.5	1
8787	1948-07-30	HORNEPAYNE	ONT	6053575	-84.77	49.2	335	13.9	14.8	-0.9	1
8788	1948-10-12	HORNEPAYNE	ONT	6053575	-84.77	49.2	335	6.1	7.2	-1.1	1
8789	1948-10-13	HORNEPAYNE	ONT	6053575	-84.77	49.2	335	6.1	6.6	-0.5	1
8790	1948-10-19	HORNEPAYNE	ONT	6053575	-84.77	49.2	335	-2.2	-0.8	-1.4	1
8791	1948-11-06	HORNEPAYNE	ONT	6053575	-84.77	49.2	335	7.2	8.9	-1.7	1
8792	1948-11-07	HORNEPAYNE	ONT	6053575	-84.77	49.2	335	2.8	2.9	-0.1	1
8793	1948-11-17	HORNEPAYNE	ONT	6053575	-84.77	49.2	335	0	1.9	-1.9	1
8794	1948-11-20	HORNEPAYNE	ONT	6053575	-84.77	49.2	335	-6.7	-6.2	-0.5	1
8795	1948-12-06	HORNEPAYNE	ONT	6053575	-84.77	49.2	335	0.6	1.3	-0.7	1
8796	1948-12-07	HORNEPAYNE	ONT	6053575	-84.77	49.2	335	-4.4	-3.6	-0.8	1
8797	1949-01-16	HORNEPAYNE	ONT	6053575	-84.77	49.2	335	-15.6	-15.2	-0.4	1
8798	1949-01-19	HORNEPAYNE	ONT	6053575	-84.77	49.2	335	-25	-21.9	-3.1	1
8799	1949-01-24	HORNEPAYNE	ONT	6053575	-84.77	49.2	335	-20	-19.1	-0.9	1
8800	1949-01-28	HORNEPAYNE	ONT	6053575	-84.77	49.2	335	-21.1	-19.6	-1.5	1
8801	1949-04-13	HORNEPAYNE	ONT	6053575	-84.77	49.2	335	-1.7	-0.9	-0.8	1
8802	1949-05-18	HORNEPAYNE	ONT	6053575	-84.77	49.2	335	5.6	6.6	-1	1
8803	1949-07-29	HORNEPAYNE	ONT	6053575	-84.77	49.2	335	12.2	13.2	-1	1
8804	1949-09-05	HORNEPAYNE	ONT	6053575	-84.77	49.2	335	8.9	9.9	-1	1
8805	1949-09-27	HORNEPAYNE	ONT	6053575	-84.77	49.2	335	9.4	10.7	-1.3	1

8806	1949-10-11	HORNEPAYNE	ONT	6053575	-84.77	49.2	335	12.2	13.2	-1	1
8807	1949-10-20	HORNEPAYNE	ONT	6053575	-84.77	49.2	335	1.1	2.9	-1.8	1
8808	1949-10-23	HORNEPAYNE	ONT	6053575	-84.77	49.2	335	1.7	1.9	-0.2	1
8809	1949-11-30	HORNEPAYNE	ONT	6053575	-84.77	49.2	335	-6.7	-6.3	-0.4	1
8810	1949-12-04	HORNEPAYNE	ONT	6053575	-84.77	49.2	335	-3.9	-3	-0.9	1
8811	1949-12-13	HORNEPAYNE	ONT	6053575	-84.77	49.2	335	-19.4	-19.1	-0.3	1
8812	1915-11-16	ANNAPOLIS ROYAL	NS	8200100	-65.52	44.75	8	3	3.7	-0.7	1
8813	1916-03-11	ANNAPOLIS ROYAL	NS	8200100	-65.52	44.75	8	-0.9	-0.5	-0.4	1
8814	1916-04-10	ANNAPOLIS ROYAL	NS	8200100	-65.52	44.75	8	-0.9	-0.5	-0.4	1
8815	1917-10-12	ANNAPOLIS ROYAL	NS	8200100	-65.52	44.75	8	4.3	5.6	-1.3	1
8816	1919-04-24	ANNAPOLIS ROYAL	NS	8200100	-65.52	44.75	8	3	4.5	-1.5	1
8817	1920-02-24	ANNAPOLIS ROYAL	NS	8200100	-65.52	44.75	8	-1.5	-1.3	-0.2	1
8818	1920-12-13	ANNAPOLIS ROYAL	NS	8200100	-65.52	44.75	8	-0.3	0	-0.3	1
8819	1921-11-03	ANNAPOLIS ROYAL	NS	8200100	-65.52	44.75	8	4.9	5.1	-0.2	1
8820	1922-11-01	ANNAPOLIS ROYAL	NS	8200100	-65.52	44.75	8	5.6	6	-0.4	1
8821	1922-11-20	ANNAPOLIS ROYAL	NS	8200100	-65.52	44.75	8	4.3	5.6	-1.3	1
8822	1922-11-21	ANNAPOLIS ROYAL	NS	8200100	-65.52	44.75	8	3	4.5	-1.5	1
8823	1922-12-18	ANNAPOLIS ROYAL	NS	8200100	-65.52	44.75	8	-2.5	-2.3	-0.2	1
8824	1922-12-22	ANNAPOLIS ROYAL	NS	8200100	-65.52	44.75	8	-0.3	0.8	-1.1	1
8825	1924-09-02	ANNAPOLIS ROYAL	NS	8200100	-65.52	44.75	8	16.6	17.4	-0.8	1
8826	1924-09-19	ANNAPOLIS ROYAL	NS	8200100	-65.52	44.75	8	16	16.2	-0.2	1
8827	1925-10-23	ANNAPOLIS ROYAL	NS	8200100	-65.52	44.75	8	4.2	4.5	-0.3	1
8828	1926-03-25	ANNAPOLIS ROYAL	NS	8200100	-65.52	44.75	8	6.4	6.6	-0.2	1
8829	1926-12-12	ANNAPOLIS ROYAL	NS	8200100	-65.52	44.75	8	-0.9	-0.5	-0.4	1
8830	1928-01-10	ANNAPOLIS ROYAL	NS	8200100	-65.52	44.75	8	4.3	4.5	-0.2	1
8831	1928-09-14	ANNAPOLIS ROYAL	NS	8200100	-65.52	44.75	8	15.3	15.4	-0.1	1
8832	1928-12-14	ANNAPOLIS ROYAL	NS	8200100	-65.52	44.75	8	3.6	3.7	-0.1	1
8833	1931-06-01	ANNAPOLIS ROYAL	NS	8200100	-65.52	44.75	8	15.9	16.1	-0.2	1
8834	1932-08-20	ANNAPOLIS ROYAL	NS	8200100	-65.52	44.75	8	20.6	21.4	-0.8	1
8835	1932-12-01	ANNAPOLIS ROYAL	NS	8200100	-65.52	44.75	8	3.5	3.7	-0.2	1
8836	1933-02-15	ANNAPOLIS ROYAL	NS	8200100	-65.52	44.75	8	3	3.8	-0.8	1
8837	1994-01-05	ANNAPOLIS ROYAL	NS	8200100	-65.52	44.75	8	-9	-6.5	-2.5	1
8838	1994-01-14	ANNAPOLIS ROYAL	NS	8200100	-65.52	44.75	8	-16	-3	-13	1
8839	1994-01-18	ANNAPOLIS ROYAL	NS	8200100	-65.52	44.75	8	-9.5	-9	-0.5	1

8840	1994-01-21	ANNAPOLIS ROYAL	NS	8200100	-65.52	44.75	8	-13.5	-11	-2.5	1
8841	1994-01-24	ANNAPOLIS ROYAL	NS	8200100	-65.52	44.75	8	-18	-15	-3	1
8842	1994-01-29	ANNAPOLIS ROYAL	NS	8200100	-65.52	44.75	8	-8	3	-11	1
8843	1999-12-21	ANNAPOLIS ROYAL	NS	8200100	-65.52	44.75	8	0.5	1	-0.5	1
8844	2000-10-15	ANNAPOLIS ROYAL	NS	8200100	-65.52	44.75	8	10	11	-1	1
8845	2001-01-17	ANNAPOLIS ROYAL	NS	8200100	-65.52	44.75	8	-6	-2.5	-3.5	1
8846	1934-06-15	PICKLE LAKE	ONT	6016529	-90.22	51.45	386	12.2	13	-0.8	1
8847	1934-06-19	PICKLE LAKE	ONT	6016529	-90.22	51.45	386	15	15.1	-0.1	1
8848	1934-08-02	PICKLE LAKE	ONT	6016529	-90.22	51.45	386	16.1	16.2	-0.1	1
8849	1934-09-26	PICKLE LAKE	ONT	6016529	-90.22	51.45	386	4.4	5.1	-0.7	1
8850	1935-06-04	PICKLE LAKE	ONT	6016529	-90.22	51.45	386	1.7	2.2	-0.5	1
8851	1935-07-05	PICKLE LAKE	ONT	6016529	-90.22	51.45	386	10.6	12	-1.4	1
8852	1935-07-31	PICKLE LAKE	ONT	6016529	-90.22	51.45	386	15.6	16.8	-1.2	1
8853	1935-08-19	PICKLE LAKE	ONT	6016529	-90.22	51.45	386	16.1	16.2	-0.1	1
8854	1935-08-20	PICKLE LAKE	ONT	6016529	-90.22	51.45	386	8.9	9.6	-0.7	1
8855	1935-08-27	PICKLE LAKE	ONT	6016529	-90.22	51.45	386	5	6.2	-1.2	1
8856	1941-05-04	PICKLE LAKE	ONT	6016529	-90.22	51.45	386	6.7	6.8	-0.1	1
8857	1947-08-05	PICKLE LAKE	ONT	6016529	-90.22	51.45	386	12.2	13.7	-1.5	1
8858	1947-08-14	PICKLE LAKE	ONT	6016529	-90.22	51.45	386	11.1	12.2	-1.1	1
8859	1947-12-29	PICKLE LAKE	ONT	6016529	-90.22	51.45	386	-21.1	-20.3	-0.8	1
8860	1948-02-21	PICKLE LAKE	ONT	6016529	-90.22	51.45	386	-18.9	-14.3	-4.6	1
8861	1948-02-22	PICKLE LAKE	ONT	6016529	-90.22	51.45	386	-12.2	-6.6	-5.6	1
8862	1948-07-05	PICKLE LAKE	ONT	6016529	-90.22	51.45	386	21.1	24.1	-3	1
8863	1948-10-16	PICKLE LAKE	ONT	6016529	-90.22	51.45	386	-3.3	-2.4	-0.9	1
8864	1948-10-19	PICKLE LAKE	ONT	6016529	-90.22	51.45	386	0	5.3	-5.3	1
8865	1948-12-14	PICKLE LAKE	ONT	6016529	-90.22	51.45	386	-14.4	-12.2	-2.2	1
8866	1948-12-27	PICKLE LAKE	ONT	6016529	-90.22	51.45	386	-13.3	-8.9	-4.4	1
8867	1949-01-24	PICKLE LAKE	ONT	6016529	-90.22	51.45	386	-20	-15.6	-4.4	1
8868	1949-03-21	PICKLE LAKE	ONT	6016529	-90.22	51.45	386	-11.1	-4.8	-6.3	1
8869	1949-03-22	PICKLE LAKE	ONT	6016529	-90.22	51.45	386	-5	-4.2	-0.8	1
8870	1949-09-14	PICKLE LAKE	ONT	6016529	-90.22	51.45	386	2.2	4	-1.8	1
8871	1949-09-15	PICKLE LAKE	ONT	6016529	-90.22	51.45	386	5.6	6.5	-0.9	1
8872	1949-10-25	PICKLE LAKE	ONT	6016529	-90.22	51.45	386	-1.7	1.4	-3.1	1
8873	1949-11-24	PICKLE LAKE	ONT	6016529	-90.22	51.45	386	-17.8	-2.9	-14.9	1

8874	1949-11-25	PICKLE LAKE	ONT	6016529	-90.22	51.45	386	-24.4	-10.6	-13.8	1
8875	1949-12-23	PICKLE LAKE	ONT	6016529	-90.22	51.45	386	-27.8	-21.7	-6.1	1
8876	1949-12-26	PICKLE LAKE	ONT	6016529	-90.22	51.45	386	-19.4	-18.2	-1.2	1
8877	1950-01-21	PICKLE LAKE	ONT	6016529	-90.22	51.45	386	-25.6	-24.5	-1.1	1
8878	1950-02-24	PICKLE LAKE	ONT	6016529	-90.22	51.45	386	-18.3	-10.6	-7.7	1
8879	1950-06-20	PICKLE LAKE	ONT	6016529	-90.22	51.45	386	9.4	12.2	-2.8	1
8880	1950-07-18	PICKLE LAKE	ONT	6016529	-90.22	51.45	386	20	21.9	-1.9	1
8881	1950-09-22	PICKLE LAKE	ONT	6016529	-90.22	51.45	386	10	12.2	-2.2	1
8882	1950-10-02	PICKLE LAKE	ONT	6016529	-90.22	51.45	386	3.9	4	-0.1	1
8883	1950-10-23	PICKLE LAKE	ONT	6016529	-90.22	51.45	386	1.1	3.9	-2.8	1
8884	1950-12-06	PICKLE LAKE	ONT	6016529	-90.22	51.45	386	-12.2	-11.1	-1.1	1
8885	1950-12-19	PICKLE LAKE	ONT	6016529	-90.22	51.45	386	-20.6	-17.4	-3.2	1
8886	1951-01-20	PICKLE LAKE	ONT	6016529	-90.22	51.45	386	-18.9	-15.6	-3.3	1
8887	1951-02-13	PICKLE LAKE	ONT	6016529	-90.22	51.45	386	-17.8	-14.8	-3	1
8888	1951-03-23	PICKLE LAKE	ONT	6016529	-90.22	51.45	386	-5.6	1.4	-7	1
8889	1956-09-23	PICKLE LAKE	ONT	6016529	-90.22	51.45	386	6.1	7.6	-1.5	1
8890	1956-12-06	PICKLE LAKE	ONT	6016529	-90.22	51.45	386	-26.1	-25.4	-0.7	1
8891	1958-08-29	PICKLE LAKE	ONT	6016529	-90.22	51.45	386	8.3	8.7	-0.4	1
8892	1958-10-24	PICKLE LAKE	ONT	6016529	-90.22	51.45	386	3.9	4	-0.1	1
8893	1960-11-02	PICKLE LAKE	ONT	6016529	-90.22	51.45	386	-0.6	-0.4	-0.2	1
8894	1963-02-02	PICKLE LAKE	ONT	6016529	-90.22	51.45	386	-28.3	-28	-0.3	1
8895	1963-08-12	PICKLE LAKE	ONT	6016529	-90.22	51.45	386	11.1	11.6	-0.5	1
8896	1963-08-22	PICKLE LAKE	ONT	6016529	-90.22	51.45	386	11.7	12.2	-0.5	1
8897	1965-08-30	PICKLE LAKE	ONT	6016529	-90.22	51.45	386	9.4	10.5	-1.1	1
8898	1980-12-19	PICKLE LAKE	ONT	6016529	-90.22	51.45	386	-24.6	-24.5	-0.1	1
8899	1981-02-19	PICKLE LAKE	ONT	6016529	-90.22	51.45	386	0.7	0.8	-0.1	1
8900	2013-02-27	PICKLE LAKE	ONT	6016529	-90.22	51.45	386	-8.1	-7.9	-0.2	1
8901	2015-08-16	PICKLE LAKE	ONT	6016529	-90.22	51.45	386	17.2	19.5	-2.3	1
8902	2015-08-23	PICKLE LAKE	ONT	6016529	-90.22	51.45	386	8.4	16.4	-8	1
8903	1984-02-08	HAINES JUNCTION	YT	2100630	-137.5	60.75	595	-18	-16	-2	1
8904	1887-01-02	ORANGEVILLE	ONT	6155790	-80.08	43.92	412	-18.9	-18.6	-0.3	1
8905	1887-12-10	ORANGEVILLE	ONT	6155790	-80.08	43.92	412	0.6	1.7	-1.1	1
8906	1888-01-17	ORANGEVILLE	ONT	6155790	-80.08	43.92	412	-12.2	-11.7	-0.5	1
8907	1897-03-19	ORANGEVILLE	ONT	6155790	-80.08	43.92	412	2.2	2.9	-0.7	1

8908	1906-11-22	ORANGEVILLE	ONT	6155790	-80.08	43.92	412	1.7	2.3	-0.6	1
8909	2007-11-21	ORANGEVILLE	ONT	6155790	-80.08	43.92	412	2	9	-7	1
8910	2007-11-27	ORANGEVILLE	ONT	6155790	-80.08	43.92	412	-7	-1	-6	1
8911	2007-11-30	ORANGEVILLE	ONT	6155790	-80.08	43.92	412	-12	-8.5	-3.5	1
8912	2008-01-01	ORANGEVILLE	ONT	6155790	-80.08	43.92	412	-3	-2	-1	1
8913	2008-12-10	ORANGEVILLE	ONT	6155790	-80.08	43.92	412	-8.5	-5	-3.5	1
8914	2008-12-18	ORANGEVILLE	ONT	6155790	-80.08	43.92	412	-5	-4	-1	1
8915	2009-02-27	ORANGEVILLE	ONT	6155790	-80.08	43.92	412	-13	0	-13	1
8916	2010-01-08	ORANGEVILLE	ONT	6155790	-80.08	43.92	412	-12.5	-9.5	-3	1
8917	2012-10-27	ORANGEVILLE	ONT	6155790	-80.08	43.92	412	1	2	-1	1
8918	2013-01-30	ORANGEVILLE	ONT	6155790	-80.08	43.92	412	-5	-4	-1	1
8919	2013-04-10	ORANGEVILLE	ONT	6155790	-80.08	43.92	412	-2	-1	-1	1
8920	2014-01-19	ORANGEVILLE	ONT	6155790	-80.08	43.92	412	-10	-9	-1	1
8921	2014-03-11	ORANGEVILLE	ONT	6155790	-80.08	43.92	412	-3	-2	-1	1
8922	2014-10-16	ORANGEVILLE	ONT	6155790	-80.08	43.92	412	7	10	-3	1
8923	2014-10-20	ORANGEVILLE	ONT	6155790	-80.08	43.92	412	2	5	-3	1
8924	2014-10-21	ORANGEVILLE	ONT	6155790	-80.08	43.92	412	0.5	1	-0.5	1
8925	2014-11-30	ORANGEVILLE	ONT	6155790	-80.08	43.92	412	-1	2	-3	1
8926	2015-11-29	ORANGEVILLE	ONT	6155790	-80.08	43.92	412	1	1.5	-0.5	1
8927	1939-03-17	VAL MARIE	SASK	4038400	-107.85	49.37	808	-13.9	-12.1	-1.8	1
8928	1959-11-16	VAL MARIE	SASK	4038400	-107.85	49.37	808	-15	-13.7	-1.3	1
8929	1970-12-28	VAL MARIE	SASK	4038400	-107.85	49.37	808	-8.3	-7.9	-0.4	1
8930	1994-02-05	VAL MARIE	SASK	4038400	-107.85	49.37	808	-23	-18	-5	1
8931	2008-11-06	VAL MARIE	SASK	4038400	-107.85	49.37	808	0	0.5	-0.5	1
8932	2008-12-07	VAL MARIE	SASK	4038400	-107.85	49.37	808	-4	-2	-2	1
8933	2008-12-11	VAL MARIE	SASK	4038400	-107.85	49.37	808	-4	-3	-1	1
8934	1984-05-29	FORT GOOD HOPE	NWT	2201450	-128.65	66.23	82	5.5	7.5	-2	1
8935	1986-01-29	GRAND FALLS	NFLD	8404310	-55.67	48.93	46	-1	0	-1	1
8936	1901-12-18	ESTEVAN	SASK	4012400	-102.97	49.22	580	-22.3	-20.5	-1.8	1
8937	1902-12-31	ESTEVAN	SASK	4012400	-102.97	49.22	580	-5.9	-5.8	-0.1	1
8938	1904-02-20	ESTEVAN	SASK	4012400	-102.97	49.22	580	-19.3	-18.1	-1.2	1
8939	1904-03-02	ESTEVAN	SASK	4012400	-102.97	49.22	580	-15.1	-14.5	-0.6	1
8940	1906-01-01	ESTEVAN	SASK	4012400	-102.97	49.22	580	-17.5	-16.8	-0.7	1
8941	1906-01-02	ESTEVAN	SASK	4012400	-102.97	49.22	580	-15.1	-15	-0.1	1

8942	1906-11-12	ESTEVAN	SASK	4012400	-102.97	49.22	580	-11.3	-10.4	-0.9	1
8943	1906-11-19	ESTEVAN	SASK	4012400	-102.97	49.22	580	-16.3	-15	-1.3	1
8944	1909-01-01	ESTEVAN	SASK	4012400	-102.97	49.22	580	-11.8	-11.4	-0.4	1
8945	1913-12-12	ESTEVAN	SASK	4012400	-102.97	49.22	580	-5.3	-5.1	-0.2	1
8946	1915-02-13	ESTEVAN	SASK	4012400	-102.97	49.22	580	-8	-7.6	-0.4	1
8947	1915-12-29	ESTEVAN	SASK	4012400	-102.97	49.22	580	-18.2	-18.1	-0.1	1
8948	1915-12-30	ESTEVAN	SASK	4012400	-102.97	49.22	580	-21	-18.7	-2.3	1
8949	1916-01-01	ESTEVAN	SASK	4012400	-102.97	49.22	580	-17	-16.8	-0.2	1
8950	1936-01-11	ESTEVAN	SASK	4012400	-102.97	49.22	580	-18.2	-16.8	-1.4	1
8951	1948-02-16	ESTEVAN	SASK	4012400	-102.97	49.22	580	-17.2	-14.9	-2.3	1
8952	1948-02-24	ESTEVAN	SASK	4012400	-102.97	49.22	580	-14.9	-6	-8.9	1
8953	2001-01-04	ESTEVAN	SASK	4012400	-102.97	49.22	580	-3.5	-2.7	-0.8	1
8954	1952-01-24	BATTLE HARBOUR	NFLD	8502592	-55.6	52.25	11	-4.7	-3.6	-1.1	1
8955	1952-11-26	BATTLE HARBOUR	NFLD	8502592	-55.6	52.25	11	-1.1	-0.4	-0.7	1
8956	2017-04-27	BATTLE HARBOUR	NFLD	8502592	-55.6	52.25	11	-3.7	-0.1	-3.6	1
8957	1872-01-19	HAMILTON	ONT	6153193	-79.93	43.17	238	-2.1	-1.1	-1	1
8958	1872-10-26	HAMILTON	ONT	6153193	-79.93	43.17	238	8.3	8.8	-0.5	1
8959	1874-02-11	HAMILTON	ONT	6153193	-79.93	43.17	238	-0.8	-0.1	-0.7	1
8960	1876-06-09	HAMILTON	ONT	6153193	-79.93	43.17	238	13.5	15	-1.5	1
8961	1876-07-11	HAMILTON	ONT	6153193	-79.93	43.17	238	18.4	19.2	-0.8	1
8962	1877-12-04	HAMILTON	ONT	6153193	-79.93	43.17	238	2.8	3.5	-0.7	1
8963	1877-12-29	HAMILTON	ONT	6153193	-79.93	43.17	238	1.2	2.9	-1.7	1
8964	1878-01-25	HAMILTON	ONT	6153193	-79.93	43.17	238	-3.4	-1.1	-2.3	1
8965	1878-02-24	HAMILTON	ONT	6153193	-79.93	43.17	238	-4.4	-2.4	-2	1
8966	1878-03-12	HAMILTON	ONT	6153193	-79.93	43.17	238	2.3	2.9	-0.6	1
8967	1878-09-12	HAMILTON	ONT	6153193	-79.93	43.17	238	12	12.1	-0.1	1
8968	1878-12-12	HAMILTON	ONT	6153193	-79.93	43.17	238	-2.8	-2.4	-0.4	1
8969	1881-03-04	HAMILTON	ONT	6153193	-79.93	43.17	238	-1.6	-1.3	-0.3	1
8970	1882-03-18	HAMILTON	ONT	6153193	-79.93	43.17	238	2	2.4	-0.4	1
8971	1882-05-28	HAMILTON	ONT	6153193	-79.93	43.17	238	4.3	5.7	-1.4	1
8972	1883-02-15	HAMILTON	ONT	6153193	-79.93	43.17	238	-1.6	0.9	-2.5	1
8973	1883-10-28	HAMILTON	ONT	6153193	-79.93	43.17	238	8.7	12.3	-3.6	1
8974	1884-03-10	HAMILTON	ONT	6153193	-79.93	43.17	238	4.7	6.5	-1.8	1
8975	1884-08-04	HAMILTON	ONT	6153193	-79.93	43.17	238	25.4	27.6	-2.2	1

8976	1885-09-01	HAMILTON	ONT	6153193	-79.93	43.17	238	5.7	7.5	-1.8	1
8977	1885-10-12	HAMILTON	ONT	6153193	-79.93	43.17	238	9.2	12.2	-3	1
8978	1885-11-27	HAMILTON	ONT	6153193	-79.93	43.17	238	-5.2	-2.5	-2.7	1
8979	1885-12-17	HAMILTON	ONT	6153193	-79.93	43.17	238	-3.5	-3.4	-0.1	1
8980	1886-04-26	HAMILTON	ONT	6153193	-79.93	43.17	238	6.9	8.2	-1.3	1
8981	1888-04-29	HAMILTON	ONT	6153193	-79.93	43.17	238	9.8	10.5	-0.7	1
8982	1897-10-20	HAMILTON	ONT	6153193	-79.93	43.17	238	9.8	12.3	-2.5	1
8983	1897-10-22	HAMILTON	ONT	6153193	-79.93	43.17	238	10.3	10.5	-0.2	1
8984	1897-11-02	HAMILTON	ONT	6153193	-79.93	43.17	238	3.9	4.3	-0.4	1
8985	1897-11-06	HAMILTON	ONT	6153193	-79.93	43.17	238	4.2	4.9	-0.7	1
8986	1897-11-09	HAMILTON	ONT	6153193	-79.93	43.17	238	1.6	2.4	-0.8	1
8987	1897-11-12	HAMILTON	ONT	6153193	-79.93	43.17	238	1.5	1.7	-0.2	1
8988	1897-11-17	HAMILTON	ONT	6153193	-79.93	43.17	238	-1.6	-1.3	-0.3	1
8989	1897-11-18	HAMILTON	ONT	6153193	-79.93	43.17	238	-1.6	-0.6	-1	1
8990	1897-12-13	HAMILTON	ONT	6153193	-79.93	43.17	238	2.5	3.8	-1.3	1
8991	1897-12-14	HAMILTON	ONT	6153193	-79.93	43.17	238	3.1	5.3	-2.2	1
8992	1897-12-15	HAMILTON	ONT	6153193	-79.93	43.17	238	3	4.9	-1.9	1
8993	1924-11-07	HAMILTON	ONT	6153193	-79.93	43.17	238	2.4	14.3	-11.9	1
8994	1938-11-30	HAMILTON	ONT	6153193	-79.93	43.17	238	1.2	1.8	-0.6	1
8995	1938-12-18	HAMILTON	ONT	6153193	-79.93	43.17	238	-3.6	-3.5	-0.1	1
8996	1939-01-08	HAMILTON	ONT	6153193	-79.93	43.17	238	1.2	1.8	-0.6	1
8997	1939-03-01	HAMILTON	ONT	6153193	-79.93	43.17	238	-1.7	-1.2	-0.5	1
8998	1939-03-30	HAMILTON	ONT	6153193	-79.93	43.17	238	-0.5	0.1	-0.6	1
8999	1939-12-20	HAMILTON	ONT	6153193	-79.93	43.17	238	2.2	2.3	-0.1	1
9000	1941-12-20	HAMILTON	ONT	6153193	-79.93	43.17	238	-4.2	-3.5	-0.7	1
9001	1942-02-01	HAMILTON	ONT	6153193	-79.93	43.17	238	-8.2	-8	-0.2	1
9002	1942-11-13	HAMILTON	ONT	6153193	-79.93	43.17	238	-0.5	0.1	-0.6	1
9003	1943-01-12	HAMILTON	ONT	6153193	-79.93	43.17	238	-5.9	-4.9	-1	1
9004	1943-02-11	HAMILTON	ONT	6153193	-79.93	43.17	238	-4.2	-3.5	-0.7	1
9005	1943-02-24	HAMILTON	ONT	6153193	-79.93	43.17	238	1.7	1.8	-0.1	1
9006	1944-02-18	HAMILTON	ONT	6153193	-79.93	43.17	238	-7.7	-6.9	-0.8	1
9007	1944-02-28	HAMILTON	ONT	6153193	-79.93	43.17	238	-2.5	-1.9	-0.6	1
9008	1944-03-18	HAMILTON	ONT	6153193	-79.93	43.17	238	-3.6	-3.1	-0.5	1
9009	1944-12-21	HAMILTON	ONT	6153193	-79.93	43.17	238	-9.9	-9.8	-0.1	1

9010	1945-01-24	HAMILTON	ONT	6153193	-79.93	43.17	238	-9.3	-8	-1.3	1
9011	1945-04-26	HAMILTON	ONT	6153193	-79.93	43.17	238	5.6	5.8	-0.2	1
9012	1945-05-10	HAMILTON	ONT	6153193	-79.93	43.17	238	2.6	2.9	-0.3	1
9013	1946-01-26	HAMILTON	ONT	6153193	-79.93	43.17	238	-10.4	-9.8	-0.6	1
9014	1946-10-12	HAMILTON	ONT	6153193	-79.93	43.17	238	8.7	8.8	-0.1	1
9015	1946-10-17	HAMILTON	ONT	6153193	-79.93	43.17	238	8.7	8.8	-0.1	1
9016	1946-12-25	HAMILTON	ONT	6153193	-79.93	43.17	238	-7.1	-5.9	-1.2	1
9017	1947-01-03	HAMILTON	ONT	6153193	-79.93	43.17	238	-8.8	-7.5	-1.3	1
9018	1947-02-04	HAMILTON	ONT	6153193	-79.93	43.17	238	-8.2	-7.5	-0.7	1
9019	1947-12-18	HAMILTON	ONT	6153193	-79.93	43.17	238	-8.2	-8	-0.2	1
9020	1948-01-13	HAMILTON	ONT	6153193	-79.93	43.17	238	-7.1	-6.9	-0.2	1
9021	1950-02-22	HAMILTON	ONT	6153193	-79.93	43.17	238	-18.2	-18.1	-0.1	1
9022	1950-03-01	HAMILTON	ONT	6153193	-79.93	43.17	238	-7.7	-7.5	-0.2	1
9023	1950-11-02	HAMILTON	ONT	6153193	-79.93	43.17	238	11.7	11.8	-0.1	1
9024	1950-11-17	HAMILTON	ONT	6153193	-79.93	43.17	238	1.7	2.3	-0.6	1
9025	1951-01-06	HAMILTON	ONT	6153193	-79.93	43.17	238	-2.4	-1.9	-0.5	1
9026	1951-01-24	HAMILTON	ONT	6153193	-79.93	43.17	238	-1.1	-0.5	-0.6	1
9027	1951-01-26	HAMILTON	ONT	6153193	-79.93	43.17	238	-7.7	-7.5	-0.2	1
9028	1951-01-27	HAMILTON	ONT	6153193	-79.93	43.17	238	-13.2	-12.3	-0.9	1
9029	1951-02-13	HAMILTON	ONT	6153193	-79.93	43.17	238	-2.4	-1.9	-0.5	1
9030	1952-01-28	HAMILTON	ONT	6153193	-79.93	43.17	238	-8.2	-7.5	-0.7	1
9031	1953-12-15	HAMILTON	ONT	6153193	-79.93	43.17	238	-3.6	-3.5	-0.1	1
9032	1953-12-30	HAMILTON	ONT	6153193	-79.93	43.17	238	-5.3	-5	-0.3	1
9033	1954-01-27	HAMILTON	ONT	6153193	-79.93	43.17	238	-5.3	-5	-0.3	1
9034	1955-12-15	HAMILTON	ONT	6153193	-79.93	43.17	238	-8.2	-8	-0.2	1
9035	1957-11-23	HAMILTON	ONT	6153193	-79.93	43.17	238	1.6	1.8	-0.2	1
9036	1994-06-18	HOPEDALE	NFLD	8502400	-60.22	55.45	12	10.5	25.9	-15.4	1
9037	1994-06-19	HOPEDALE	NFLD	8502400	-60.22	55.45	12	8.8	25.9	-17.1	1
9038	2003-07-28	HOPEDALE	NFLD	8502400	-60.22	55.45	12	12.9	14.1	-1.2	1
9039	2003-08-17	HOPEDALE	NFLD	8502400	-60.22	55.45	12	11.4	14.3	-2.9	1
9040	2003-08-21	HOPEDALE	NFLD	8502400	-60.22	55.45	12	10.5	12.2	-1.7	1
9041	2003-09-15	HOPEDALE	NFLD	8502400	-60.22	55.45	12	9	11.6	-2.6	1
9042	1908-08-10	PEACE RIVER	ALTA	3075041	-117.43	56.23	571	11.1	11.7	-0.6	1
9043	1910-12-03	PEACE RIVER	ALTA	3075041	-117.43	56.23	571	-15.3	-15	-0.3	1

9044	1911-01-20	PEACE RIVER	ALTA	3075041	-117.43	56.23	571	-27.5	-26.5	-1	1
9045	1911-01-23	PEACE RIVER	ALTA	3075041	-117.43	56.23	571	-28.7	-27.5	-1.2	1
9046	1911-01-30	PEACE RIVER	ALTA	3075041	-117.43	56.23	571	-28.1	-23.8	-4.3	1
9047	1911-05-18	PEACE RIVER	ALTA	3075041	-117.43	56.23	571	6.8	8.5	-1.7	1
9048	1912-09-17	PEACE RIVER	ALTA	3075041	-117.43	56.23	571	11.6	11.7	-0.1	1
9049	1912-10-08	PEACE RIVER	ALTA	3075041	-117.43	56.23	571	2.9	5.2	-2.3	1
9050	1912-11-03	PEACE RIVER	ALTA	3075041	-117.43	56.23	571	-1.8	-1.5	-0.3	1
9051	1912-11-05	PEACE RIVER	ALTA	3075041	-117.43	56.23	571	-1.8	-1.5	-0.3	1
9052	1913-05-01	PEACE RIVER	ALTA	3075041	-117.43	56.23	571	7.9	8.4	-0.5	1
9053	1913-06-13	PEACE RIVER	ALTA	3075041	-117.43	56.23	571	5.2	7.4	-2.2	1
9054	1913-06-14	PEACE RIVER	ALTA	3075041	-117.43	56.23	571	5.7	8.9	-3.2	1
9055	1913-06-15	PEACE RIVER	ALTA	3075041	-117.43	56.23	571	4.9	5.6	-0.7	1
9056	1913-09-21	PEACE RIVER	ALTA	3075041	-117.43	56.23	571	6.2	8.4	-2.2	1
9057	1914-06-21	PEACE RIVER	ALTA	3075041	-117.43	56.23	571	8.4	8.9	-0.5	1
9058	1918-06-14	PEACE RIVER	ALTA	3075041	-117.43	56.23	571	9	9.5	-0.5	1
9059	1919-05-30	PEACE RIVER	ALTA	3075041	-117.43	56.23	571	3	3.2	-0.2	1
9060	1920-01-14	PEACE RIVER	ALTA	3075041	-117.43	56.23	571	-19.3	-19.1	-0.2	1
9061	1920-05-11	PEACE RIVER	ALTA	3075041	-117.43	56.23	571	2.5	2.7	-0.2	1
9062	1922-04-22	PEACE RIVER	ALTA	3075041	-117.43	56.23	571	2.9	3.2	-0.3	1
9063	1925-04-04	PEACE RIVER	ALTA	3075041	-117.43	56.23	571	1.5	2.1	-0.6	1
9064	1928-03-07	PEACE RIVER	ALTA	3075041	-117.43	56.23	571	-13.3	-12.6	-0.7	1
9065	1930-06-26	PEACE RIVER	ALTA	3075041	-117.43	56.23	571	11.6	12.3	-0.7	1
9066	1932-02-13	PEACE RIVER	ALTA	3075041	-117.43	56.23	571	-24.8	-24.3	-0.5	1
9067	1999-01-25	PEACE RIVER	ALTA	3075041	-117.43	56.23	571	-15.5	-13.9	-1.6	1
9068	2007-07-20	ATLIN	BC	1200560	-133.7	59.57	674	9.5	10.5	-1	1
9069	1937-09-16	ARCTIC BAY	NU	2400404	-84.62	72.98	10	-5.9	-3.5	-2.4	1
9070	1937-09-18	ARCTIC BAY	NU	2400404	-84.62	72.98	10	-5.3	-3.5	-1.8	1
9071	1937-09-19	ARCTIC BAY	NU	2400404	-84.62	72.98	10	-4.9	-4.5	-0.4	1
9072	1937-09-20	ARCTIC BAY	NU	2400404	-84.62	72.98	10	-2.8	-2.5	-0.3	1
9073	1937-09-21	ARCTIC BAY	NU	2400404	-84.62	72.98	10	-2.8	-0.3	-2.5	1
9074	1937-09-22	ARCTIC BAY	NU	2400404	-84.62	72.98	10	-3.4	-2.5	-0.9	1
9075	1937-09-24	ARCTIC BAY	NU	2400404	-84.62	72.98	10	-6.1	-4.5	-1.6	1
9076	1937-09-25	ARCTIC BAY	NU	2400404	-84.62	72.98	10	-6.1	-5	-1.1	1
9077	1937-10-04	ARCTIC BAY	NU	2400404	-84.62	72.98	10	-6.1	-4.5	-1.6	1

9078	1937-10-05	ARCTIC BAY	NU	2400404	-84.62	72.98	10	-7.4	-6.8	-0.6	1
9079	1937-10-06	ARCTIC BAY	NU	2400404	-84.62	72.98	10	-9.3	-9.2	-0.1	1
9080	1937-10-07	ARCTIC BAY	NU	2400404	-84.62	72.98	10	-8.9	-8.7	-0.2	1
9081	1937-10-08	ARCTIC BAY	NU	2400404	-84.62	72.98	10	-9.3	-9.2	-0.1	1
9082	1938-05-16	ARCTIC BAY	NU	2400404	-84.62	72.98	10	-2.8	-1.9	-0.9	1
9083	1938-05-17	ARCTIC BAY	NU	2400404	-84.62	72.98	10	-3.4	-1.9	-1.5	1
9084	1938-05-19	ARCTIC BAY	NU	2400404	-84.62	72.98	10	-4.4	-2.9	-1.5	1
9085	1938-05-24	ARCTIC BAY	NU	2400404	-84.62	72.98	10	-3.4	-2.9	-0.5	1
9086	1938-05-30	ARCTIC BAY	NU	2400404	-84.62	72.98	10	-1.1	-0.9	-0.2	1
9087	1938-05-31	ARCTIC BAY	NU	2400404	-84.62	72.98	10	-1.6	-0.3	-1.3	1
9088	1938-06-01	ARCTIC BAY	NU	2400404	-84.62	72.98	10	-5.8	-5	-0.8	1
9089	1938-06-03	ARCTIC BAY	NU	2400404	-84.62	72.98	10	-4.4	-2.5	-1.9	1
9090	1938-06-05	ARCTIC BAY	NU	2400404	-84.62	72.98	10	-3.4	-1.9	-1.5	1
9091	1938-06-07	ARCTIC BAY	NU	2400404	-84.62	72.98	10	-2.3	-0.9	-1.4	1
9092	1938-06-16	ARCTIC BAY	NU	2400404	-84.62	72.98	10	1	2.5	-1.5	1
9093	1938-06-20	ARCTIC BAY	NU	2400404	-84.62	72.98	10	1	2.5	-1.5	1
9094	1938-06-21	ARCTIC BAY	NU	2400404	-84.62	72.98	10	1.7	1.8	-0.1	1
9095	1938-06-22	ARCTIC BAY	NU	2400404	-84.62	72.98	10	1.8	2.5	-0.7	1
9096	1938-06-25	ARCTIC BAY	NU	2400404	-84.62	72.98	10	3.8	4.9	-1.1	1
9097	1938-07-02	ARCTIC BAY	NU	2400404	-84.62	72.98	10	2.4	3.1	-0.7	1
9098	1938-07-27	ARCTIC BAY	NU	2400404	-84.62	72.98	10	3.8	4.3	-0.5	1
9099	1938-07-29	ARCTIC BAY	NU	2400404	-84.62	72.98	10	3.2	4.3	-1.1	1
9100	1938-09-04	ARCTIC BAY	NU	2400404	-84.62	72.98	10	-0.4	-0.2	-0.2	1
9101	1938-09-05	ARCTIC BAY	NU	2400404	-84.62	72.98	10	-0.4	1.2	-1.6	1
9102	1938-09-06	ARCTIC BAY	NU	2400404	-84.62	72.98	10	-2.3	-0.2	-2.1	1
9103	1938-09-07	ARCTIC BAY	NU	2400404	-84.62	72.98	10	-3.9	-2.5	-1.4	1
9104	1938-09-08	ARCTIC BAY	NU	2400404	-84.62	72.98	10	-4.4	-2.9	-1.5	1
9105	1938-09-09	ARCTIC BAY	NU	2400404	-84.62	72.98	10	-4.4	-2.5	-1.9	1
9106	1938-09-10	ARCTIC BAY	NU	2400404	-84.62	72.98	10	-4.9	-2.4	-2.5	1
9107	1938-09-11	ARCTIC BAY	NU	2400404	-84.62	72.98	10	-3.9	-3.5	-0.4	1
9108	1938-09-12	ARCTIC BAY	NU	2400404	-84.62	72.98	10	-2.8	-2.4	-0.4	1
9109	1938-09-14	ARCTIC BAY	NU	2400404	-84.62	72.98	10	-5.3	-2.4	-2.9	1
9110	1938-09-25	ARCTIC BAY	NU	2400404	-84.62	72.98	10	-8.9	-8.7	-0.2	1
9111	1938-09-26	ARCTIC BAY	NU	2400404	-84.62	72.98	10	-9.2	-8	-1.2	1

9112	1938-09-30	ARCTIC BAY	NU	2400404	-84.62	72.98	10	-9.2	-8.6	-0.6	1
9113	1939-09-24	ARCTIC BAY	NU	2400404	-84.62	72.98	10	-2.3	-0.2	-2.1	1
9114	1939-10-02	ARCTIC BAY	NU	2400404	-84.62	72.98	10	-5.4	-3.9	-1.5	1
9115	1939-10-04	ARCTIC BAY	NU	2400404	-84.62	72.98	10	-5.8	-5	-0.8	1
9116	1940-04-18	ARCTIC BAY	NU	2400404	-84.62	72.98	10	-10.5	-10.3	-0.2	1
9117	1940-05-15	ARCTIC BAY	NU	2400404	-84.62	72.98	10	-8.4	-8	-0.4	1
9118	1940-05-22	ARCTIC BAY	NU	2400404	-84.62	72.98	10	-2.8	-1.5	-1.3	1
9119	1940-05-23	ARCTIC BAY	NU	2400404	-84.62	72.98	10	-1.6	-0.2	-1.4	1
9120	1940-08-10	ARCTIC BAY	NU	2400404	-84.62	72.98	10	1.7	2.6	-0.9	1
9121	1940-08-18	ARCTIC BAY	NU	2400404	-84.62	72.98	10	0.2	0.4	-0.2	1
9122	1940-08-19	ARCTIC BAY	NU	2400404	-84.62	72.98	10	-0.3	0.4	-0.7	1
9123	1940-08-21	ARCTIC BAY	NU	2400404	-84.62	72.98	10	1.7	1.9	-0.2	1
9124	1940-08-25	ARCTIC BAY	NU	2400404	-84.62	72.98	10	2.5	4.3	-1.8	1
9125	1940-10-01	ARCTIC BAY	NU	2400404	-84.62	72.98	10	-5.8	-5.6	-0.2	1
9126	1940-10-11	ARCTIC BAY	NU	2400404	-84.62	72.98	10	-8.9	-8	-0.9	1
9127	1940-10-12	ARCTIC BAY	NU	2400404	-84.62	72.98	10	-9.3	-9.2	-0.1	1
9128	1940-10-31	ARCTIC BAY	NU	2400404	-84.62	72.98	10	-7	-6.8	-0.2	1
9129	1940-12-30	ARCTIC BAY	NU	2400404	-84.62	72.98	10	-17.9	-17.3	-0.6	1
9130	1941-06-03	ARCTIC BAY	NU	2400404	-84.62	72.98	10	-7.5	-6.8	-0.7	1
9131	1941-06-10	ARCTIC BAY	NU	2400404	-84.62	72.98	10	-5.3	-5	-0.3	1
9132	1941-06-11	ARCTIC BAY	NU	2400404	-84.62	72.98	10	-3.9	-3.5	-0.4	1
9133	1941-06-12	ARCTIC BAY	NU	2400404	-84.62	72.98	10	-2.8	-2.5	-0.3	1
9134	1941-06-18	ARCTIC BAY	NU	2400404	-84.62	72.98	10	-2.8	-1.9	-0.9	1
9135	1941-06-19	ARCTIC BAY	NU	2400404	-84.62	72.98	10	-1.7	-1.5	-0.2	1
9136	1941-06-20	ARCTIC BAY	NU	2400404	-84.62	72.98	10	-1.1	-0.9	-0.2	1
9137	1941-06-23	ARCTIC BAY	NU	2400404	-84.62	72.98	10	-1.7	-0.9	-0.8	1
9138	1941-09-04	ARCTIC BAY	NU	2400404	-84.62	72.98	10	-1	-0.9	-0.1	1
9139	1941-09-06	ARCTIC BAY	NU	2400404	-84.62	72.98	10	-4.4	-3.9	-0.5	1
9140	1941-09-11	ARCTIC BAY	NU	2400404	-84.62	72.98	10	-0.3	1.2	-1.5	1
9141	1941-09-12	ARCTIC BAY	NU	2400404	-84.62	72.98	10	-4.9	-2.9	-2	1
9142	1941-09-14	ARCTIC BAY	NU	2400404	-84.62	72.98	10	-5.8	-5.6	-0.2	1
9143	1941-09-15	ARCTIC BAY	NU	2400404	-84.62	72.98	10	-5.3	-5	-0.3	1
9144	1941-09-19	ARCTIC BAY	NU	2400404	-84.62	72.98	10	-7	-6.8	-0.2	1
9145	1941-10-30	ARCTIC BAY	NU	2400404	-84.62	72.98	10	-9.3	-8.6	-0.7	1

9146	1942-06-01	ARCTIC BAY	NU	2400404	-84.62	72.98	10	-6.2	-5.6	-0.6	1
9147	1942-06-15	ARCTIC BAY	NU	2400404	-84.62	72.98	10	-1.1	-0.9	-0.2	1
9148	1942-06-16	ARCTIC BAY	NU	2400404	-84.62	72.98	10	-1.1	-0.2	-0.9	1
9149	1942-06-25	ARCTIC BAY	NU	2400404	-84.62	72.98	10	0.2	1.2	-1	1
9150	1942-07-26	ARCTIC BAY	NU	2400404	-84.62	72.98	10	-2.3	-0.9	-1.4	1
9151	1942-08-05	ARCTIC BAY	NU	2400404	-84.62	72.98	10	1.6	2.6	-1	1
9152	1942-08-06	ARCTIC BAY	NU	2400404	-84.62	72.98	10	-1	-0.9	-0.1	1
9153	1942-08-24	ARCTIC BAY	NU	2400404	-84.62	72.98	10	0.2	0.5	-0.3	1
9154	1942-09-08	ARCTIC BAY	NU	2400404	-84.62	72.98	10	-3.4	-2.9	-0.5	1
9155	1942-09-10	ARCTIC BAY	NU	2400404	-84.62	72.98	10	-4.9	-4.5	-0.4	1
9156	1942-09-17	ARCTIC BAY	NU	2400404	-84.62	72.98	10	-3.4	-2.9	-0.5	1
9157	1942-09-18	ARCTIC BAY	NU	2400404	-84.62	72.98	10	-6.7	-6.3	-0.4	1
9158	1942-09-24	ARCTIC BAY	NU	2400404	-84.62	72.98	10	-6.2	-5.6	-0.6	1
9159	1942-09-29	ARCTIC BAY	NU	2400404	-84.62	72.98	10	-5.8	-4.5	-1.3	1
9160	1942-10-04	ARCTIC BAY	NU	2400404	-84.62	72.98	10	-9.3	-9.2	-0.1	1
9161	1943-06-15	ARCTIC BAY	NU	2400404	-84.62	72.98	10	2.3	3.2	-0.9	1
9162	1943-06-18	ARCTIC BAY	NU	2400404	-84.62	72.98	10	2.3	2.5	-0.2	1
9163	1943-07-10	ARCTIC BAY	NU	2400404	-84.62	72.98	10	1.8	2.6	-0.8	1
9164	1943-09-01	ARCTIC BAY	NU	2400404	-84.62	72.98	10	3.8	4.3	-0.5	1
9165	1943-09-02	ARCTIC BAY	NU	2400404	-84.62	72.98	10	4.7	4.9	-0.2	1
9166	1943-09-05	ARCTIC BAY	NU	2400404	-84.62	72.98	10	-0.4	-0.2	-0.2	1
9167	1943-09-06	ARCTIC BAY	NU	2400404	-84.62	72.98	10	-1.6	-1.5	-0.1	1
9168	1943-09-07	ARCTIC BAY	NU	2400404	-84.62	72.98	10	-4.4	-2.5	-1.9	1
9169	1943-09-08	ARCTIC BAY	NU	2400404	-84.62	72.98	10	-3.8	-2.9	-0.9	1
9170	1943-09-10	ARCTIC BAY	NU	2400404	-84.62	72.98	10	-2.3	-1.5	-0.8	1
9171	1943-09-11	ARCTIC BAY	NU	2400404	-84.62	72.98	10	-3.4	-2.9	-0.5	1
9172	1943-09-13	ARCTIC BAY	NU	2400404	-84.62	72.98	10	-3.4	-1.5	-1.9	1
9173	1943-09-14	ARCTIC BAY	NU	2400404	-84.62	72.98	10	-2.8	-1.9	-0.9	1
9174	1943-09-21	ARCTIC BAY	NU	2400404	-84.62	72.98	10	-4.9	-4.5	-0.4	1
9175	1943-09-22	ARCTIC BAY	NU	2400404	-84.62	72.98	10	-7.1	-5	-2.1	1
9176	1943-09-25	ARCTIC BAY	NU	2400404	-84.62	72.98	10	-3.4	-2.9	-0.5	1
9177	1943-09-26	ARCTIC BAY	NU	2400404	-84.62	72.98	10	-6.7	-6.3	-0.4	1
9178	1943-10-01	ARCTIC BAY	NU	2400404	-84.62	72.98	10	-7.1	-5.6	-1.5	1
9179	1943-10-19	ARCTIC BAY	NU	2400404	-84.62	72.98	10	-4.4	-3.4	-1	1

9180	1944-06-09	ARCTIC BAY	NU	2400404	-84.62	72.98	10	-1.1	-0.9	-0.2	1
9181	1944-08-21	ARCTIC BAY	NU	2400404	-84.62	72.98	10	-0.4	0.3	-0.7	1
9182	1944-08-24	ARCTIC BAY	NU	2400404	-84.62	72.98	10	-2.8	-1.9	-0.9	1
9183	1944-09-01	ARCTIC BAY	NU	2400404	-84.62	72.98	10	3.1	3.8	-0.7	1
9184	1944-09-02	ARCTIC BAY	NU	2400404	-84.62	72.98	10	1.7	2.6	-0.9	1
9185	1944-09-04	ARCTIC BAY	NU	2400404	-84.62	72.98	10	2.5	3.2	-0.7	1
9186	1944-09-18	ARCTIC BAY	NU	2400404	-84.62	72.98	10	-5.3	-5	-0.3	1
9187	1944-09-20	ARCTIC BAY	NU	2400404	-84.62	72.98	10	-6.2	-5	-1.2	1
9188	1944-09-23	ARCTIC BAY	NU	2400404	-84.62	72.98	10	-4.4	-3.9	-0.5	1
9189	1944-10-09	ARCTIC BAY	NU	2400404	-84.62	72.98	10	-6.2	-5	-1.2	1
9190	1944-10-21	ARCTIC BAY	NU	2400404	-84.62	72.98	10	-18.5	-18.4	-0.1	1
9191	1944-11-05	ARCTIC BAY	NU	2400404	-84.62	72.98	10	-19.5	-18.4	-1.1	1
9192	1944-11-08	ARCTIC BAY	NU	2400404	-84.62	72.98	10	-21.6	-21.5	-0.1	1
9193	1944-11-15	ARCTIC BAY	NU	2400404	-84.62	72.98	10	-10.1	-8.6	-1.5	1
9194	1944-11-18	ARCTIC BAY	NU	2400404	-84.62	72.98	10	-8.4	-7.4	-1	1
9195	1945-03-22	ARCTIC BAY	NU	2400404	-84.62	72.98	10	-11.4	-10.9	-0.5	1
9196	1945-06-05	ARCTIC BAY	NU	2400404	-84.62	72.98	10	-2.3	-1.9	-0.4	1
9197	1945-06-14	ARCTIC BAY	NU	2400404	-84.62	72.98	10	-2.3	-0.9	-1.4	1
9198	1945-06-16	ARCTIC BAY	NU	2400404	-84.62	72.98	10	-2.8	-2.5	-0.3	1
9199	1945-08-30	ARCTIC BAY	NU	2400404	-84.62	72.98	10	-0.3	0.4	-0.7	1
9200	1945-09-04	ARCTIC BAY	NU	2400404	-84.62	72.98	10	-1.1	-0.9	-0.2	1
9201	1945-09-07	ARCTIC BAY	NU	2400404	-84.62	72.98	10	-5.3	-3.9	-1.4	1
9202	1945-09-09	ARCTIC BAY	NU	2400404	-84.62	72.98	10	-5.3	-4.5	-0.8	1
9203	1945-09-13	ARCTIC BAY	NU	2400404	-84.62	72.98	10	-6.7	-5.6	-1.1	1
9204	1945-09-16	ARCTIC BAY	NU	2400404	-84.62	72.98	10	-5.8	-4.5	-1.3	1
9205	1945-09-19	ARCTIC BAY	NU	2400404	-84.62	72.98	10	-4.4	-3.9	-0.5	1
9206	1945-09-23	ARCTIC BAY	NU	2400404	-84.62	72.98	10	-6.7	-5.6	-1.1	1
9207	1945-09-24	ARCTIC BAY	NU	2400404	-84.62	72.98	10	-7.5	-6.2	-1.3	1
9208	1945-09-25	ARCTIC BAY	NU	2400404	-84.62	72.98	10	-8.9	-8.6	-0.3	1
9209	1945-10-01	ARCTIC BAY	NU	2400404	-84.62	72.98	10	-10.1	-9.2	-0.9	1
9210	1945-10-15	ARCTIC BAY	NU	2400404	-84.62	72.98	10	-7.5	-6.8	-0.7	1
9211	1945-10-29	ARCTIC BAY	NU	2400404	-84.62	72.98	10	-13.5	-13	-0.5	1
9212	1945-11-01	ARCTIC BAY	NU	2400404	-84.62	72.98	10	-11.8	-10.9	-0.9	1
9213	1945-11-11	ARCTIC BAY	NU	2400404	-84.62	72.98	10	-18.5	-18.4	-0.1	1

9214	1946-05-11	ARCTIC BAY	NU	2400404	-84.62	72.98	10	-6.2	-5	-1.2	1
9215	1946-06-04	ARCTIC BAY	NU	2400404	-84.62	72.98	10	-4.9	-4.5	-0.4	1
9216	1946-08-20	ARCTIC BAY	NU	2400404	-84.62	72.98	10	1.8	1.9	-0.1	1
9217	1946-08-30	ARCTIC BAY	NU	2400404	-84.62	72.98	10	1.8	3.1	-1.3	1
9218	1946-09-07	ARCTIC BAY	NU	2400404	-84.62	72.98	10	-0.4	-0.3	-0.1	1
9219	1946-09-09	ARCTIC BAY	NU	2400404	-84.62	72.98	10	-0.4	-0.3	-0.1	1
9220	1946-09-10	ARCTIC BAY	NU	2400404	-84.62	72.98	10	-2.8	-2.5	-0.3	1
9221	1946-09-11	ARCTIC BAY	NU	2400404	-84.62	72.98	10	-6.2	-2.9	-3.3	1
9222	1946-09-12	ARCTIC BAY	NU	2400404	-84.62	72.98	10	-4.9	-4.5	-0.4	1
9223	1946-09-13	ARCTIC BAY	NU	2400404	-84.62	72.98	10	-4.4	-3.5	-0.9	1
9224	1946-09-15	ARCTIC BAY	NU	2400404	-84.62	72.98	10	-6.7	-5	-1.7	1
9225	1946-09-16	ARCTIC BAY	NU	2400404	-84.62	72.98	10	-5.8	-5.6	-0.2	1
9226	1946-09-17	ARCTIC BAY	NU	2400404	-84.62	72.98	10	-5.3	-5	-0.3	1
9227	1946-09-19	ARCTIC BAY	NU	2400404	-84.62	72.98	10	-7.9	-7.4	-0.5	1
9228	1946-09-20	ARCTIC BAY	NU	2400404	-84.62	72.98	10	-8.8	-8.6	-0.2	1
9229	1946-09-23	ARCTIC BAY	NU	2400404	-84.62	72.98	10	-8.4	-7.4	-1	1
9230	1946-09-30	ARCTIC BAY	NU	2400404	-84.62	72.98	10	-9.2	-8.6	-0.6	1
9231	1946-10-02	ARCTIC BAY	NU	2400404	-84.62	72.98	10	-5.3	-3.9	-1.4	1
9232	1946-10-09	ARCTIC BAY	NU	2400404	-84.62	72.98	10	-7.1	-6.3	-0.8	1
9233	1946-10-11	ARCTIC BAY	NU	2400404	-84.62	72.98	10	-6.7	-5.6	-1.1	1
9234	1947-06-01	ARCTIC BAY	NU	2400404	-84.62	72.98	10	-2.3	-0.9	-1.4	1
9235	1947-06-03	ARCTIC BAY	NU	2400404	-84.62	72.98	10	-3.4	-1.5	-1.9	1
9236	1947-06-05	ARCTIC BAY	NU	2400404	-84.62	72.98	10	-4.4	-2.9	-1.5	1
9237	1947-06-11	ARCTIC BAY	NU	2400404	-84.62	72.98	10	-3.8	-2.9	-0.9	1
9238	1947-06-13	ARCTIC BAY	NU	2400404	-84.62	72.98	10	-3.4	-2.9	-0.5	1
9239	1947-06-18	ARCTIC BAY	NU	2400404	-84.62	72.98	10	-0.4	1.3	-1.7	1
9240	1947-07-22	ARCTIC BAY	NU	2400404	-84.62	72.98	10	0.2	1.2	-1	1
9241	1947-08-19	ARCTIC BAY	NU	2400404	-84.62	72.98	10	4.6	4.9	-0.3	1
9242	1947-08-21	ARCTIC BAY	NU	2400404	-84.62	72.98	10	2.3	2.5	-0.2	1
9243	1947-08-22	ARCTIC BAY	NU	2400404	-84.62	72.98	10	1.7	2.6	-0.9	1
9244	1947-08-24	ARCTIC BAY	NU	2400404	-84.62	72.98	10	-0.4	0.4	-0.8	1
9245	1947-08-25	ARCTIC BAY	NU	2400404	-84.62	72.98	10	0.2	1.8	-1.6	1
9246	1947-08-27	ARCTIC BAY	NU	2400404	-84.62	72.98	10	-0.4	1.2	-1.6	1
9247	1947-08-31	ARCTIC BAY	NU	2400404	-84.62	72.98	10	0.2	1.2	-1	1

9248	1947-09-01	ARCTIC BAY	NU	2400404	-84.62	72.98	10	-1.6	1.2	-2.8	1
9249	1947-09-02	ARCTIC BAY	NU	2400404	-84.62	72.98	10	-1.6	-1.5	-0.1	1
9250	1947-09-05	ARCTIC BAY	NU	2400404	-84.62	72.98	10	-2.8	-0.9	-1.9	1
9251	1947-09-07	ARCTIC BAY	NU	2400404	-84.62	72.98	10	-4.4	-1.9	-2.5	1
9252	1947-09-08	ARCTIC BAY	NU	2400404	-84.62	72.98	10	-4.4	-2.4	-2	1
9253	1947-09-09	ARCTIC BAY	NU	2400404	-84.62	72.98	10	-4.4	-2.4	-2	1
9254	1947-09-12	ARCTIC BAY	NU	2400404	-84.62	72.98	10	-4.4	-3.5	-0.9	1
9255	1947-09-14	ARCTIC BAY	NU	2400404	-84.62	72.98	10	-4.4	-1.9	-2.5	1
9256	1947-09-15	ARCTIC BAY	NU	2400404	-84.62	72.98	10	-4.4	-2.9	-1.5	1
9257	1947-09-16	ARCTIC BAY	NU	2400404	-84.62	72.98	10	-4.9	-3.5	-1.4	1
9258	1947-09-17	ARCTIC BAY	NU	2400404	-84.62	72.98	10	-5.3	-5	-0.3	1
9259	1947-09-21	ARCTIC BAY	NU	2400404	-84.62	72.98	10	-6.1	-5	-1.1	1
9260	1947-09-22	ARCTIC BAY	NU	2400404	-84.62	72.98	10	-5.8	-4.5	-1.3	1
9261	1947-09-23	ARCTIC BAY	NU	2400404	-84.62	72.98	10	-7.9	-6.8	-1.1	1
9262	1947-09-24	ARCTIC BAY	NU	2400404	-84.62	72.98	10	-7.9	-7.5	-0.4	1
9263	1947-09-26	ARCTIC BAY	NU	2400404	-84.62	72.98	10	-5.3	-4.5	-0.8	1
9264	1947-09-27	ARCTIC BAY	NU	2400404	-84.62	72.98	10	-5.8	-5	-0.8	1
9265	1947-10-01	ARCTIC BAY	NU	2400404	-84.62	72.98	10	-5.8	-5.6	-0.2	1
9266	1947-10-02	ARCTIC BAY	NU	2400404	-84.62	72.98	10	-7	-5	-2	1
9267	1947-10-03	ARCTIC BAY	NU	2400404	-84.62	72.98	10	-9.6	-9.2	-0.4	1
9268	1947-10-14	ARCTIC BAY	NU	2400404	-84.62	72.98	10	-8.9	-8.7	-0.2	1
9269	1947-10-21	ARCTIC BAY	NU	2400404	-84.62	72.98	10	-4.9	-2.4	-2.5	1
9270	1947-10-22	ARCTIC BAY	NU	2400404	-84.62	72.98	10	-7.5	-6.3	-1.2	1
9271	1947-10-23	ARCTIC BAY	NU	2400404	-84.62	72.98	10	-10.1	-9.8	-0.3	1
9272	1947-11-11	ARCTIC BAY	NU	2400404	-84.62	72.98	10	-4.4	-2.5	-1.9	1
9273	1948-05-01	ARCTIC BAY	NU	2400404	-84.62	72.98	10	-6.6	-4.5	-2.1	1
9274	1948-05-10	ARCTIC BAY	NU	2400404	-84.62	72.98	10	-5.3	-3.9	-1.4	1
9275	1948-06-01	ARCTIC BAY	NU	2400404	-84.62	72.98	10	-2.8	-0.9	-1.9	1
9276	1948-06-02	ARCTIC BAY	NU	2400404	-84.62	72.98	10	-2.8	-1.5	-1.3	1
9277	1948-06-14	ARCTIC BAY	NU	2400404	-84.62	72.98	10	-1.6	-0.3	-1.3	1
9278	1948-09-01	ARCTIC BAY	NU	2400404	-84.62	72.98	10	1.7	2.6	-0.9	1
9279	1948-09-05	ARCTIC BAY	NU	2400404	-84.62	72.98	10	-2.3	-1.5	-0.8	1
9280	1948-09-07	ARCTIC BAY	NU	2400404	-84.62	72.98	10	-2.8	-2.5	-0.3	1
9281	1948-09-08	ARCTIC BAY	NU	2400404	-84.62	72.98	10	-4.9	-3.4	-1.5	1

9282	1948-09-12	ARCTIC BAY	NU	2400404	-84.62	72.98	10	-1.6	-0.9	-0.7	1
9283	1948-09-18	ARCTIC BAY	NU	2400404	-84.62	72.98	10	-3.8	-2.9	-0.9	1
9284	1948-09-25	ARCTIC BAY	NU	2400404	-84.62	72.98	10	-0.4	1.1	-1.5	1
9285	1948-09-26	ARCTIC BAY	NU	2400404	-84.62	72.98	10	-2.3	-1.5	-0.8	1
9286	1948-09-27	ARCTIC BAY	NU	2400404	-84.62	72.98	10	-6.6	-5	-1.6	1
9287	1948-09-30	ARCTIC BAY	NU	2400404	-84.62	72.98	10	-4.9	-4.5	-0.4	1
9288	1948-11-02	ARCTIC BAY	NU	2400404	-84.62	72.98	10	-5.3	-4.5	-0.8	1
9289	1949-06-22	ARCTIC BAY	NU	2400404	-84.62	72.98	10	0.2	1.8	-1.6	1
9290	1949-07-08	ARCTIC BAY	NU	2400404	-84.62	72.98	10	-0.4	0.4	-0.8	1
9291	1949-09-06	ARCTIC BAY	NU	2400404	-84.62	72.98	10	-1.1	-0.3	-0.8	1
9292	1949-09-16	ARCTIC BAY	NU	2400404	-84.62	72.98	10	-2.3	-1.5	-0.8	1
9293	1949-09-17	ARCTIC BAY	NU	2400404	-84.62	72.98	10	-1.6	-1.5	-0.1	1
9294	1949-09-18	ARCTIC BAY	NU	2400404	-84.62	72.98	10	-2.8	-1.5	-1.3	1
9295	1949-09-19	ARCTIC BAY	NU	2400404	-84.62	72.98	10	-3.8	-3.5	-0.3	1
9296	1950-05-19	ARCTIC BAY	NU	2400404	-84.62	72.98	10	-5.8	-5.6	-0.2	1
9297	1950-08-12	ARCTIC BAY	NU	2400404	-84.62	72.98	10	-0.4	0.3	-0.7	1
9298	1950-09-01	ARCTIC BAY	NU	2400404	-84.62	72.98	10	2.5	3.1	-0.6	1
9299	1950-09-02	ARCTIC BAY	NU	2400404	-84.62	72.98	10	1	1.1	-0.1	1
9300	1950-09-05	ARCTIC BAY	NU	2400404	-84.62	72.98	10	-2.8	-0.9	-1.9	1
9301	1950-09-08	ARCTIC BAY	NU	2400404	-84.62	72.98	10	-4.9	-4.5	-0.4	1
9302	1950-09-11	ARCTIC BAY	NU	2400404	-84.62	72.98	10	-1.6	-1.5	-0.1	1
9303	1950-09-13	ARCTIC BAY	NU	2400404	-84.62	72.98	10	-5.8	-4.5	-1.3	1
9304	1950-09-24	ARCTIC BAY	NU	2400404	-84.62	72.98	10	-2.8	-2.5	-0.3	1
9305	1950-09-25	ARCTIC BAY	NU	2400404	-84.62	72.98	10	-3.9	-2.5	-1.4	1
9306	1950-09-26	ARCTIC BAY	NU	2400404	-84.62	72.98	10	-3.9	-2.9	-1	1
9307	1950-09-27	ARCTIC BAY	NU	2400404	-84.62	72.98	10	-6.7	-6.3	-0.4	1
9308	1951-06-10	ARCTIC BAY	NU	2400404	-84.62	72.98	10	-1.1	1.8	-2.9	1
9309	1951-06-11	ARCTIC BAY	NU	2400404	-84.62	72.98	10	0.9	1.1	-0.2	1
9310	1951-06-12	ARCTIC BAY	NU	2400404	-84.62	72.98	10	-0.3	1.8	-2.1	1
9311	1951-06-18	ARCTIC BAY	NU	2400404	-84.62	72.98	10	-0.3	-0.2	-0.1	1
9312	1951-07-30	ARCTIC BAY	NU	2400404	-84.62	72.98	10	0.3	1.9	-1.6	1
9313	1951-08-15	ARCTIC BAY	NU	2400404	-84.62	72.98	10	2.4	2.5	-0.1	1
9314	1951-08-19	ARCTIC BAY	NU	2400404	-84.62	72.98	10	-1.7	-0.9	-0.8	1
9315	1951-08-20	ARCTIC BAY	NU	2400404	-84.62	72.98	10	0.3	0.4	-0.1	1

9316	1951-08-21	ARCTIC BAY	NU	2400404	-84.62	72.98	10	-1.1	-0.9	-0.2	1
9317	1951-09-05	ARCTIC BAY	NU	2400404	-84.62	72.98	10	-3.4	-2.9	-0.5	1
9318	1951-09-07	ARCTIC BAY	NU	2400404	-84.62	72.98	10	0.9	1.3	-0.4	1
9319	1951-09-18	ARCTIC BAY	NU	2400404	-84.62	72.98	10	-2.3	0.3	-2.6	1
9320	1951-09-19	ARCTIC BAY	NU	2400404	-84.62	72.98	10	-1	-0.9	-0.1	1
9321	1951-09-21	ARCTIC BAY	NU	2400404	-84.62	72.98	10	-6.1	-4.5	-1.6	1
9322	1951-09-22	ARCTIC BAY	NU	2400404	-84.62	72.98	10	-6.7	-5	-1.7	1
9323	1951-09-23	ARCTIC BAY	NU	2400404	-84.62	72.98	10	-5.3	-4.5	-0.8	1
9324	1951-09-24	ARCTIC BAY	NU	2400404	-84.62	72.98	10	-5.8	-5.6	-0.2	1
9325	1951-09-25	ARCTIC BAY	NU	2400404	-84.62	72.98	10	-6.7	-5.6	-1.1	1
9326	1951-09-26	ARCTIC BAY	NU	2400404	-84.62	72.98	10	-5.8	-5.6	-0.2	1
9327	1951-09-27	ARCTIC BAY	NU	2400404	-84.62	72.98	10	-6.1	-5	-1.1	1
9328	1951-09-28	ARCTIC BAY	NU	2400404	-84.62	72.98	10	-7	-6.3	-0.7	1
9329	1951-09-29	ARCTIC BAY	NU	2400404	-84.62	72.98	10	-8.9	-8	-0.9	1
9330	1951-09-30	ARCTIC BAY	NU	2400404	-84.62	72.98	10	-9.3	-8.7	-0.6	1
9331	1952-01-25	ARCTIC BAY	NU	2400404	-84.62	72.98	10	-18.9	-14.6	-4.3	1
9332	1952-06-10	ARCTIC BAY	NU	2400404	-84.62	72.98	10	0.9	1.1	-0.2	1
9333	1952-07-23	ARCTIC BAY	NU	2400404	-84.62	72.98	10	0.3	0.4	-0.1	1
9334	1952-08-19	ARCTIC BAY	NU	2400404	-84.62	72.98	10	0.2	1.2	-1	1
9335	1952-08-23	ARCTIC BAY	NU	2400404	-84.62	72.98	10	-1.6	-0.9	-0.7	1
9336	1952-08-28	ARCTIC BAY	NU	2400404	-84.62	72.98	10	-3.4	-1.5	-1.9	1
9337	1952-08-30	ARCTIC BAY	NU	2400404	-84.62	72.98	10	-1.1	1.2	-2.3	1
9338	1952-08-31	ARCTIC BAY	NU	2400404	-84.62	72.98	10	-1.6	-0.2	-1.4	1
9339	1952-09-01	ARCTIC BAY	NU	2400404	-84.62	72.98	10	-3.4	-1.5	-1.9	1
9340	1952-09-02	ARCTIC BAY	NU	2400404	-84.62	72.98	10	-2.3	-1.9	-0.4	1
9341	1952-09-03	ARCTIC BAY	NU	2400404	-84.62	72.98	10	-2.3	-0.9	-1.4	1
9342	1952-09-04	ARCTIC BAY	NU	2400404	-84.62	72.98	10	-0.4	-0.2	-0.2	1
9343	1952-09-06	ARCTIC BAY	NU	2400404	-84.62	72.98	10	-3.9	-2.9	-1	1
9344	1952-09-12	ARCTIC BAY	NU	2400404	-84.62	72.98	10	-1.6	-1.5	-0.1	1
9345	1952-09-13	ARCTIC BAY	NU	2400404	-84.62	72.98	10	-3.4	-2.5	-0.9	1
9346	1952-09-16	ARCTIC BAY	NU	2400404	-84.62	72.98	10	-1.1	1.2	-2.3	1
9347	1952-09-17	ARCTIC BAY	NU	2400404	-84.62	72.98	10	-2.3	-1.5	-0.8	1
9348	1952-09-23	ARCTIC BAY	NU	2400404	-84.62	72.98	10	-6.2	-5.6	-0.6	1
9349	1952-09-24	ARCTIC BAY	NU	2400404	-84.62	72.98	10	-6.7	-6.3	-0.4	1

9350	1952-09-25	ARCTIC BAY	NU	2400404	-84.62	72.98	10	-6.2	-5.6	-0.6	1
9351	1952-09-29	ARCTIC BAY	NU	2400404	-84.62	72.98	10	-3.4	-2.5	-0.9	1
9352	1953-04-30	ARCTIC BAY	NU	2400404	-84.62	72.98	10	-5.4	-5	-0.4	1
9353	1953-06-03	ARCTIC BAY	NU	2400404	-84.62	72.98	10	-4.4	-3.9	-0.5	1
9354	1953-06-08	ARCTIC BAY	NU	2400404	-84.62	72.98	10	-2.3	-1.5	-0.8	1
9355	1953-06-09	ARCTIC BAY	NU	2400404	-84.62	72.98	10	-2.8	-2.5	-0.3	1
9356	1953-06-10	ARCTIC BAY	NU	2400404	-84.62	72.98	10	-4.4	-3.9	-0.5	1
9357	1953-06-11	ARCTIC BAY	NU	2400404	-84.62	72.98	10	-4.9	-3.9	-1	1
9358	1953-06-22	ARCTIC BAY	NU	2400404	-84.62	72.98	10	-1.1	-0.9	-0.2	1
9359	1953-06-23	ARCTIC BAY	NU	2400404	-84.62	72.98	10	-0.4	-0.2	-0.2	1
9360	1953-06-25	ARCTIC BAY	NU	2400404	-84.62	72.98	10	1.6	1.9	-0.3	1
9361	1953-07-25	ARCTIC BAY	NU	2400404	-84.62	72.98	10	0.3	0.4	-0.1	1
9362	1953-07-26	ARCTIC BAY	NU	2400404	-84.62	72.98	10	0.3	0.4	-0.1	1
9363	1953-08-18	ARCTIC BAY	NU	2400404	-84.62	72.98	10	-1	-0.2	-0.8	1
9364	1953-09-06	ARCTIC BAY	NU	2400404	-84.62	72.98	10	-1.6	-0.2	-1.4	1
9365	1953-09-11	ARCTIC BAY	NU	2400404	-84.62	72.98	10	-5.8	-5.6	-0.2	1
9366	1953-09-14	ARCTIC BAY	NU	2400404	-84.62	72.98	10	-3.8	-3.4	-0.4	1
9367	1953-09-23	ARCTIC BAY	NU	2400404	-84.62	72.98	10	-4.9	-4.5	-0.4	1
9368	1953-09-24	ARCTIC BAY	NU	2400404	-84.62	72.98	10	-4.9	-4.5	-0.4	1
9369	1953-09-30	ARCTIC BAY	NU	2400404	-84.62	72.98	10	-6.2	-4.5	-1.7	1
9370	1954-05-10	ARCTIC BAY	NU	2400404	-84.62	72.98	10	-7.8	-7.4	-0.4	1
9371	1954-05-12	ARCTIC BAY	NU	2400404	-84.62	72.98	10	-8.8	-8	-0.8	1
9372	1954-06-06	ARCTIC BAY	NU	2400404	-84.62	72.98	10	-3.8	-2.9	-0.9	1
9373	1954-06-10	ARCTIC BAY	NU	2400404	-84.62	72.98	10	-3.8	-3.5	-0.3	1
9374	1954-06-13	ARCTIC BAY	NU	2400404	-84.62	72.98	10	-3.4	-1.9	-1.5	1
9375	1954-06-18	ARCTIC BAY	NU	2400404	-84.62	72.98	10	-1.6	-0.3	-1.3	1
9376	1954-06-20	ARCTIC BAY	NU	2400404	-84.62	72.98	10	0.2	0.4	-0.2	1
9377	1954-06-22	ARCTIC BAY	NU	2400404	-84.62	72.98	10	-2.3	-1.9	-0.4	1
9378	1954-08-31	ARCTIC BAY	NU	2400404	-84.62	72.98	10	3.2	3.8	-0.6	1
9379	1954-09-04	ARCTIC BAY	NU	2400404	-84.62	72.98	10	0.3	0.5	-0.2	1
9380	1954-09-05	ARCTIC BAY	NU	2400404	-84.62	72.98	10	1.7	1.8	-0.1	1
9381	1954-09-12	ARCTIC BAY	NU	2400404	-84.62	72.98	10	1.7	1.8	-0.1	1
9382	1954-09-13	ARCTIC BAY	NU	2400404	-84.62	72.98	10	0.3	0.4	-0.1	1
9383	1954-09-14	ARCTIC BAY	NU	2400404	-84.62	72.98	10	-2.3	-1.9	-0.4	1

9384	1954-09-15	ARCTIC BAY	NU	2400404	-84.62	72.98	10	-3.4	-2.5	-0.9	1
9385	1954-09-18	ARCTIC BAY	NU	2400404	-84.62	72.98	10	-1.1	-0.9	-0.2	1
9386	1954-09-20	ARCTIC BAY	NU	2400404	-84.62	72.98	10	-4.4	-3.9	-0.5	1
9387	1954-09-22	ARCTIC BAY	NU	2400404	-84.62	72.98	10	-6.1	-5.6	-0.5	1
9388	1954-09-26	ARCTIC BAY	NU	2400404	-84.62	72.98	10	-3.4	-1.9	-1.5	1
9389	1954-09-27	ARCTIC BAY	NU	2400404	-84.62	72.98	10	-4.9	-3.5	-1.4	1
9390	1955-02-17	ARCTIC BAY	NU	2400404	-84.62	72.98	10	-27	-26.1	-0.9	1
9391	1955-05-27	ARCTIC BAY	NU	2400404	-84.62	72.98	10	-4.4	-3.3	-1.1	1
9392	1955-05-28	ARCTIC BAY	NU	2400404	-84.62	72.98	10	-6.1	-1.7	-4.4	1
9393	1955-05-29	ARCTIC BAY	NU	2400404	-84.62	72.98	10	-6.1	-3.9	-2.2	1
9394	1955-06-05	ARCTIC BAY	NU	2400404	-84.62	72.98	10	-2.3	0	-2.3	1
9395	1955-06-09	ARCTIC BAY	NU	2400404	-84.62	72.98	10	-0.4	0	-0.4	1
9396	1955-06-11	ARCTIC BAY	NU	2400404	-84.62	72.98	10	-2.8	-0.6	-2.2	1
9397	1955-06-13	ARCTIC BAY	NU	2400404	-84.62	72.98	10	-3.4	-2.8	-0.6	1
9398	1955-06-22	ARCTIC BAY	NU	2400404	-84.62	72.98	10	0.2	2.2	-2	1
9399	1955-06-24	ARCTIC BAY	NU	2400404	-84.62	72.98	10	-1.1	0.6	-1.7	1
9400	1955-08-12	ARCTIC BAY	NU	2400404	-84.62	72.98	10	0.2	0.6	-0.4	1
9401	1955-08-27	ARCTIC BAY	NU	2400404	-84.62	72.98	10	1.8	2.2	-0.4	1
9402	1955-08-29	ARCTIC BAY	NU	2400404	-84.62	72.98	10	3.2	4.4	-1.2	1
9403	1955-08-30	ARCTIC BAY	NU	2400404	-84.62	72.98	10	0.9	3.3	-2.4	1
9404	1955-08-31	ARCTIC BAY	NU	2400404	-84.62	72.98	10	-2.8	0	-2.8	1
9405	1955-09-01	ARCTIC BAY	NU	2400404	-84.62	72.98	10	-3.4	0	-3.4	1
9406	1955-09-02	ARCTIC BAY	NU	2400404	-84.62	72.98	10	-2.3	-1.1	-1.2	1
9407	1955-09-04	ARCTIC BAY	NU	2400404	-84.62	72.98	10	-2.3	0	-2.3	1
9408	1955-09-05	ARCTIC BAY	NU	2400404	-84.62	72.98	10	-4.4	-2.8	-1.6	1
9409	1955-09-06	ARCTIC BAY	NU	2400404	-84.62	72.98	10	-4.4	-1.7	-2.7	1
9410	1955-09-07	ARCTIC BAY	NU	2400404	-84.62	72.98	10	-2.8	-1.7	-1.1	1
9411	1955-09-10	ARCTIC BAY	NU	2400404	-84.62	72.98	10	-3.9	-1.1	-2.8	1
9412	1955-09-11	ARCTIC BAY	NU	2400404	-84.62	72.98	10	-2.3	-2.2	-0.1	1
9413	1955-09-21	ARCTIC BAY	NU	2400404	-84.62	72.98	10	-4.9	-4.4	-0.5	1
9414	1955-09-23	ARCTIC BAY	NU	2400404	-84.62	72.98	10	-6.2	-6.1	-0.1	1
9415	1955-09-25	ARCTIC BAY	NU	2400404	-84.62	72.98	10	-7.1	-6.7	-0.4	1
9416	1955-09-27	ARCTIC BAY	NU	2400404	-84.62	72.98	10	-6.1	-3.9	-2.2	1
9417	1955-09-28	ARCTIC BAY	NU	2400404	-84.62	72.98	10	-7.9	-6.1	-1.8	1

9418	1955-09-29	ARCTIC BAY	NU	2400404	-84.62	72.98	10	-7.5	-7.2	-0.3	1
9419	1955-10-06	ARCTIC BAY	NU	2400404	-84.62	72.98	10	-3.4	-1.1	-2.3	1
9420	1955-10-07	ARCTIC BAY	NU	2400404	-84.62	72.98	10	-2.3	-0.6	-1.7	1
9421	1955-10-08	ARCTIC BAY	NU	2400404	-84.62	72.98	10	-2.8	0	-2.8	1
9422	1955-10-09	ARCTIC BAY	NU	2400404	-84.62	72.98	10	-2.8	0	-2.8	1
9423	1955-10-10	ARCTIC BAY	NU	2400404	-84.62	72.98	10	-5.3	-5	-0.3	1
9424	1955-10-12	ARCTIC BAY	NU	2400404	-84.62	72.98	10	-3.4	-1.1	-2.3	1
9425	1955-10-13	ARCTIC BAY	NU	2400404	-84.62	72.98	10	-2.3	-1.1	-1.2	1
9426	1955-10-16	ARCTIC BAY	NU	2400404	-84.62	72.98	10	-5.9	-5	-0.9	1
9427	1955-10-17	ARCTIC BAY	NU	2400404	-84.62	72.98	10	-7.5	-6.1	-1.4	1
9428	1955-10-19	ARCTIC BAY	NU	2400404	-84.62	72.98	10	-8.9	-8.3	-0.6	1
9429	1955-10-20	ARCTIC BAY	NU	2400404	-84.62	72.98	10	-9.7	-8.3	-1.4	1
9430	1955-10-26	ARCTIC BAY	NU	2400404	-84.62	72.98	10	-6.1	-5.6	-0.5	1
9431	1955-10-28	ARCTIC BAY	NU	2400404	-84.62	72.98	10	-3.8	-2.2	-1.6	1
9432	1955-10-29	ARCTIC BAY	NU	2400404	-84.62	72.98	10	-7	-5.6	-1.4	1
9433	1955-11-03	ARCTIC BAY	NU	2400404	-84.62	72.98	10	-3.4	-2.2	-1.2	1
9434	1955-12-28	ARCTIC BAY	NU	2400404	-84.62	72.98	10	-31.8	-26.1	-5.7	1
9435	1956-02-15	ARCTIC BAY	NU	2400404	-84.62	72.98	10	-18.5	-18.3	-0.2	1
9436	1956-02-16	ARCTIC BAY	NU	2400404	-84.62	72.98	10	-24.5	-19.4	-5.1	1
9437	1956-03-26	ARCTIC BAY	NU	2400404	-84.62	72.98	10	-30.9	-30.6	-0.3	1
9438	1956-06-03	ARCTIC BAY	NU	2400404	-84.62	72.98	10	-4.4	-3.9	-0.5	1
9439	1956-07-22	ARCTIC BAY	NU	2400404	-84.62	72.98	10	0.9	1.1	-0.2	1
9440	1956-08-18	ARCTIC BAY	NU	2400404	-84.62	72.98	10	1	2.2	-1.2	1
9441	1956-08-19	ARCTIC BAY	NU	2400404	-84.62	72.98	10	-0.4	1.7	-2.1	1
9442	1956-08-24	ARCTIC BAY	NU	2400404	-84.62	72.98	10	2.3	3.3	-1	1
9443	1956-08-25	ARCTIC BAY	NU	2400404	-84.62	72.98	10	0.9	2.2	-1.3	1
9444	1956-08-27	ARCTIC BAY	NU	2400404	-84.62	72.98	10	1	1.1	-0.1	1
9445	1956-08-28	ARCTIC BAY	NU	2400404	-84.62	72.98	10	-1.1	0	-1.1	1
9446	1956-08-29	ARCTIC BAY	NU	2400404	-84.62	72.98	10	-4.4	-0.6	-3.8	1
9447	1956-08-30	ARCTIC BAY	NU	2400404	-84.62	72.98	10	-4.9	-2.8	-2.1	1
9448	1956-09-02	ARCTIC BAY	NU	2400404	-84.62	72.98	10	-2.3	-2.2	-0.1	1
9449	1956-09-05	ARCTIC BAY	NU	2400404	-84.62	72.98	10	-1.7	-1.1	-0.6	1
9450	1956-09-06	ARCTIC BAY	NU	2400404	-84.62	72.98	10	-3.9	-1.7	-2.2	1
9451	1956-09-07	ARCTIC BAY	NU	2400404	-84.62	72.98	10	-4.4	-2.8	-1.6	1

9452	1956-09-08	ARCTIC BAY	NU	2400404	-84.62	72.98	10	-3.9	-2.8	-1.1	1
9453	1956-09-09	ARCTIC BAY	NU	2400404	-84.62	72.98	10	-6.2	-5	-1.2	1
9454	1956-09-17	ARCTIC BAY	NU	2400404	-84.62	72.98	10	-6.2	-5.6	-0.6	1
9455	1956-09-18	ARCTIC BAY	NU	2400404	-84.62	72.98	10	-6.2	-5.6	-0.6	1
9456	1956-09-19	ARCTIC BAY	NU	2400404	-84.62	72.98	10	-6.2	-5	-1.2	1
9457	1956-09-21	ARCTIC BAY	NU	2400404	-84.62	72.98	10	-2.8	-1.1	-1.7	1
9458	1956-09-22	ARCTIC BAY	NU	2400404	-84.62	72.98	10	-2.8	-1.1	-1.7	1
9459	1956-09-24	ARCTIC BAY	NU	2400404	-84.62	72.98	10	-3.4	-1.7	-1.7	1
9460	1956-09-26	ARCTIC BAY	NU	2400404	-84.62	72.98	10	-5.3	-4.4	-0.9	1
9461	1956-09-30	ARCTIC BAY	NU	2400404	-84.62	72.98	10	-7.4	-7.2	-0.2	1
9462	1956-10-31	ARCTIC BAY	NU	2400404	-84.62	72.98	10	-9.3	-8.3	-1	1
9463	1956-11-01	ARCTIC BAY	NU	2400404	-84.62	72.98	10	-9.8	-9.4	-0.4	1
9464	1957-06-03	ARCTIC BAY	NU	2400404	-84.62	72.98	10	-5.8	-5.6	-0.2	1
9465	1957-06-06	ARCTIC BAY	NU	2400404	-84.62	72.98	10	-3.9	-3.3	-0.6	1
9466	1957-06-11	ARCTIC BAY	NU	2400404	-84.62	72.98	10	-2.8	-2.2	-0.6	1
9467	1957-08-03	ARCTIC BAY	NU	2400404	-84.62	72.98	10	-0.4	0.6	-1	1
9468	1957-08-10	ARCTIC BAY	NU	2400404	-84.62	72.98	10	-2.3	-1.1	-1.2	1
9469	1957-08-11	ARCTIC BAY	NU	2400404	-84.62	72.98	10	-0.4	0	-0.4	1
9470	1957-08-16	ARCTIC BAY	NU	2400404	-84.62	72.98	10	-1.6	-1.1	-0.5	1
9471	1957-08-27	ARCTIC BAY	NU	2400404	-84.62	72.98	10	2.5	3.3	-0.8	1
9472	1957-08-28	ARCTIC BAY	NU	2400404	-84.62	72.98	10	1	1.7	-0.7	1
9473	1957-08-30	ARCTIC BAY	NU	2400404	-84.62	72.98	10	3.1	3.3	-0.2	1
9474	1957-09-04	ARCTIC BAY	NU	2400404	-84.62	72.98	10	-1.6	-1.1	-0.5	1
9475	1957-09-06	ARCTIC BAY	NU	2400404	-84.62	72.98	10	-0.4	0	-0.4	1
9476	1957-09-16	ARCTIC BAY	NU	2400404	-84.62	72.98	10	-5.3	-4.4	-0.9	1
9477	1957-09-17	ARCTIC BAY	NU	2400404	-84.62	72.98	10	-4.9	-4.4	-0.5	1
9478	1957-09-20	ARCTIC BAY	NU	2400404	-84.62	72.98	10	-1	-0.6	-0.4	1
9479	1957-09-21	ARCTIC BAY	NU	2400404	-84.62	72.98	10	-2.3	-2.2	-0.1	1
9480	1957-09-22	ARCTIC BAY	NU	2400404	-84.62	72.98	10	-2.8	-1.1	-1.7	1
9481	1957-09-23	ARCTIC BAY	NU	2400404	-84.62	72.98	10	-3.4	-2.2	-1.2	1
9482	1957-09-25	ARCTIC BAY	NU	2400404	-84.62	72.98	10	-4.9	-4.4	-0.5	1
9483	1958-05-24	ARCTIC BAY	NU	2400404	-84.62	72.98	10	-2.3	-2.2	-0.1	1
9484	1958-05-29	ARCTIC BAY	NU	2400404	-84.62	72.98	10	-1.6	-1.1	-0.5	1
9485	1958-09-06	ARCTIC BAY	NU	2400404	-84.62	72.98	10	0.2	0.6	-0.4	1

9486	1958-09-20	ARCTIC BAY	NU	2400404	-84.62	72.98	10	-5.8	-5.6	-0.2	1
9487	1958-09-27	ARCTIC BAY	NU	2400404	-84.62	72.98	10	-7.5	-7.2	-0.3	1
9488	1958-10-16	ARCTIC BAY	NU	2400404	-84.62	72.98	10	-7.4	-6.7	-0.7	1
9489	1959-09-03	ARCTIC BAY	NU	2400404	-84.62	72.98	10	0.2	0.6	-0.4	1
9490	1959-09-04	ARCTIC BAY	NU	2400404	-84.62	72.98	10	-1.1	1.1	-2.2	1
9491	1959-09-05	ARCTIC BAY	NU	2400404	-84.62	72.98	10	-2.8	0	-2.8	1
9492	1959-09-08	ARCTIC BAY	NU	2400404	-84.62	72.98	10	0.2	2.2	-2	1
9493	1959-09-09	ARCTIC BAY	NU	2400404	-84.62	72.98	10	-3.4	0	-3.4	1
9494	1959-09-10	ARCTIC BAY	NU	2400404	-84.62	72.98	10	-3.4	-1.1	-2.3	1
9495	1959-09-11	ARCTIC BAY	NU	2400404	-84.62	72.98	10	-4.4	-2.2	-2.2	1
9496	1959-09-12	ARCTIC BAY	NU	2400404	-84.62	72.98	10	-5.8	-3.3	-2.5	1
9497	1959-09-13	ARCTIC BAY	NU	2400404	-84.62	72.98	10	-4.9	-2.8	-2.1	1
9498	1959-09-14	ARCTIC BAY	NU	2400404	-84.62	72.98	10	-2.3	-2.2	-0.1	1
9499	1959-09-15	ARCTIC BAY	NU	2400404	-84.62	72.98	10	-2.3	0	-2.3	1
9500	1959-09-17	ARCTIC BAY	NU	2400404	-84.62	72.98	10	-2.3	-0.6	-1.7	1
9501	1959-09-18	ARCTIC BAY	NU	2400404	-84.62	72.98	10	-5.8	-3.3	-2.5	1
9502	1959-09-19	ARCTIC BAY	NU	2400404	-84.62	72.98	10	-6.6	-4.4	-2.2	1
9503	1959-09-20	ARCTIC BAY	NU	2400404	-84.62	72.98	10	-7.1	-5.6	-1.5	1
9504	1959-09-25	ARCTIC BAY	NU	2400404	-84.62	72.98	10	-7.5	-6.1	-1.4	1
9505	1959-09-26	ARCTIC BAY	NU	2400404	-84.62	72.98	10	-6.1	-5.6	-0.5	1
9506	1959-09-27	ARCTIC BAY	NU	2400404	-84.62	72.98	10	-9.2	-8.3	-0.9	1
9507	1959-09-29	ARCTIC BAY	NU	2400404	-84.62	72.98	10	-11.4	-10.6	-0.8	1
9508	1959-10-02	ARCTIC BAY	NU	2400404	-84.62	72.98	10	-11.7	-11.1	-0.6	1
9509	1959-10-08	ARCTIC BAY	NU	2400404	-84.62	72.98	10	-12.1	-11.7	-0.4	1
9510	1959-10-10	ARCTIC BAY	NU	2400404	-84.62	72.98	10	-13	-12.8	-0.2	1
9511	1959-10-17	ARCTIC BAY	NU	2400404	-84.62	72.98	10	-10.9	-10	-0.9	1
9512	1960-03-14	ARCTIC BAY	NU	2400404	-84.62	72.98	10	-28.2	-27.8	-0.4	1
9513	1960-06-05	ARCTIC BAY	NU	2400404	-84.62	72.98	10	-3.4	-1.1	-2.3	1
9514	1960-06-06	ARCTIC BAY	NU	2400404	-84.62	72.98	10	-3.4	-3.3	-0.1	1
9515	1960-06-07	ARCTIC BAY	NU	2400404	-84.62	72.98	10	-2.3	-1.1	-1.2	1
9516	1960-06-12	ARCTIC BAY	NU	2400404	-84.62	72.98	10	1	1.7	-0.7	1
9517	1960-06-13	ARCTIC BAY	NU	2400404	-84.62	72.98	10	1	2.8	-1.8	1
9518	1960-06-14	ARCTIC BAY	NU	2400404	-84.62	72.98	10	0.2	1.1	-0.9	1
9519	1960-06-17	ARCTIC BAY	NU	2400404	-84.62	72.98	10	1	1.7	-0.7	1

9520	1960-06-23	ARCTIC BAY	NU	2400404	-84.62	72.98	10	1	2.2	-1.2	1
9521	1960-07-03	ARCTIC BAY	NU	2400404	-84.62	72.98	10	2.4	3.9	-1.5	1
9522	1960-07-11	ARCTIC BAY	NU	2400404	-84.62	72.98	10	3.9	4.4	-0.5	1
9523	1960-07-20	ARCTIC BAY	NU	2400404	-84.62	72.98	10	4	4.4	-0.4	1
9524	1960-07-22	ARCTIC BAY	NU	2400404	-84.62	72.98	10	0.2	2.8	-2.6	1
9525	1960-07-24	ARCTIC BAY	NU	2400404	-84.62	72.98	10	2.5	3.9	-1.4	1
9526	1960-07-27	ARCTIC BAY	NU	2400404	-84.62	72.98	10	7.5	7.8	-0.3	1
9527	1960-07-28	ARCTIC BAY	NU	2400404	-84.62	72.98	10	4.6	5	-0.4	1
9528	1960-08-01	ARCTIC BAY	NU	2400404	-84.62	72.98	10	0.9	2.2	-1.3	1
9529	1960-08-13	ARCTIC BAY	NU	2400404	-84.62	72.98	10	1.7	2.8	-1.1	1
9530	1960-08-18	ARCTIC BAY	NU	2400404	-84.62	72.98	10	5.4	6.1	-0.7	1
9531	1960-08-26	ARCTIC BAY	NU	2400404	-84.62	72.98	10	3.2	5.6	-2.4	1
9532	1960-08-31	ARCTIC BAY	NU	2400404	-84.62	72.98	10	3.2	5	-1.8	1
9533	1960-09-01	ARCTIC BAY	NU	2400404	-84.62	72.98	10	1.7	3.3	-1.6	1
9534	1960-09-02	ARCTIC BAY	NU	2400404	-84.62	72.98	10	0.9	2.2	-1.3	1
9535	1960-09-03	ARCTIC BAY	NU	2400404	-84.62	72.98	10	1.7	2.2	-0.5	1
9536	1960-09-04	ARCTIC BAY	NU	2400404	-84.62	72.98	10	0.9	1.7	-0.8	1
9537	1960-09-05	ARCTIC BAY	NU	2400404	-84.62	72.98	10	0.2	1.7	-1.5	1
9538	1960-09-06	ARCTIC BAY	NU	2400404	-84.62	72.98	10	-3.4	-0.6	-2.8	1
9539	1960-09-07	ARCTIC BAY	NU	2400404	-84.62	72.98	10	-3.4	-1.1	-2.3	1
9540	1960-09-08	ARCTIC BAY	NU	2400404	-84.62	72.98	10	-4.9	-2.2	-2.7	1
9541	1960-09-09	ARCTIC BAY	NU	2400404	-84.62	72.98	10	-4.9	-2.8	-2.1	1
9542	1960-09-10	ARCTIC BAY	NU	2400404	-84.62	72.98	10	-5.4	-3.3	-2.1	1
9543	1960-09-11	ARCTIC BAY	NU	2400404	-84.62	72.98	10	-6.2	-4.4	-1.8	1
9544	1960-09-14	ARCTIC BAY	NU	2400404	-84.62	72.98	10	-5.4	-3.3	-2.1	1
9545	1960-09-15	ARCTIC BAY	NU	2400404	-84.62	72.98	10	-5.3	-2.8	-2.5	1
9546	1960-09-16	ARCTIC BAY	NU	2400404	-84.62	72.98	10	-4.4	-2.8	-1.6	1
9547	1960-09-17	ARCTIC BAY	NU	2400404	-84.62	72.98	10	-4.9	-3.9	-1	1
9548	1960-09-18	ARCTIC BAY	NU	2400404	-84.62	72.98	10	-6.1	-3.9	-2.2	1
9549	1960-09-20	ARCTIC BAY	NU	2400404	-84.62	72.98	10	-3.8	-2.2	-1.6	1
9550	1960-09-21	ARCTIC BAY	NU	2400404	-84.62	72.98	10	-4.4	-3.3	-1.1	1
9551	1960-09-23	ARCTIC BAY	NU	2400404	-84.62	72.98	10	-4.4	-1.7	-2.7	1
9552	1960-09-24	ARCTIC BAY	NU	2400404	-84.62	72.98	10	-5.7	-5	-0.7	1
9553	1960-09-25	ARCTIC BAY	NU	2400404	-84.62	72.98	10	-6.6	-3.9	-2.7	1

9554	1960-09-27	ARCTIC BAY	NU	2400404	-84.62	72.98	10	-10.1	-7.8	-2.3	1
9555	1960-10-02	ARCTIC BAY	NU	2400404	-84.62	72.98	10	-8.9	-7.8	-1.1	1
9556	1960-10-03	ARCTIC BAY	NU	2400404	-84.62	72.98	10	-7.1	-6.7	-0.4	1
9557	1960-10-04	ARCTIC BAY	NU	2400404	-84.62	72.98	10	-5.7	-5	-0.7	1
9558	1960-10-05	ARCTIC BAY	NU	2400404	-84.62	72.98	10	-5.8	-5.6	-0.2	1
9559	1960-10-07	ARCTIC BAY	NU	2400404	-84.62	72.98	10	-5.3	-3.3	-2	1
9560	1960-10-12	ARCTIC BAY	NU	2400404	-84.62	72.98	10	-12.6	-11.7	-0.9	1
9561	1960-10-15	ARCTIC BAY	NU	2400404	-84.62	72.98	10	-6.6	-6.1	-0.5	1
9562	1960-10-16	ARCTIC BAY	NU	2400404	-84.62	72.98	10	-10.5	-8.9	-1.6	1
9563	1960-10-24	ARCTIC BAY	NU	2400404	-84.62	72.98	10	-8.9	-8.3	-0.6	1
9564	1960-10-27	ARCTIC BAY	NU	2400404	-84.62	72.98	10	-8.4	-7.8	-0.6	1
9565	1961-04-23	ARCTIC BAY	NU	2400404	-84.62	72.98	10	-7.5	-7.2	-0.3	1
9566	1961-06-05	ARCTIC BAY	NU	2400404	-84.62	72.98	10	-3.9	-2.8	-1.1	1
9567	1961-06-06	ARCTIC BAY	NU	2400404	-84.62	72.98	10	-3.4	-1.7	-1.7	1
9568	1961-06-07	ARCTIC BAY	NU	2400404	-84.62	72.98	10	-6.7	-6.1	-0.6	1
9569	1961-06-15	ARCTIC BAY	NU	2400404	-84.62	72.98	10	-1.1	1.1	-2.2	1
9570	1961-06-16	ARCTIC BAY	NU	2400404	-84.62	72.98	10	-0.4	0	-0.4	1
9571	1961-06-22	ARCTIC BAY	NU	2400404	-84.62	72.98	10	0.3	1.7	-1.4	1
9572	1961-06-25	ARCTIC BAY	NU	2400404	-84.62	72.98	10	-1.1	0.6	-1.7	1
9573	1961-06-26	ARCTIC BAY	NU	2400404	-84.62	72.98	10	0.9	1.1	-0.2	1
9574	1961-06-27	ARCTIC BAY	NU	2400404	-84.62	72.98	10	-1.6	-0.6	-1	1
9575	1961-06-28	ARCTIC BAY	NU	2400404	-84.62	72.98	10	-1	0	-1	1
9576	1961-06-30	ARCTIC BAY	NU	2400404	-84.62	72.98	10	-1.6	0	-1.6	1
9577	1961-07-07	ARCTIC BAY	NU	2400404	-84.62	72.98	10	3.1	4.4	-1.3	1
9578	1961-07-11	ARCTIC BAY	NU	2400404	-84.62	72.98	10	0.3	1.7	-1.4	1
9579	1961-07-30	ARCTIC BAY	NU	2400404	-84.62	72.98	10	-0.4	0	-0.4	1
9580	1961-08-15	ARCTIC BAY	NU	2400404	-84.62	72.98	10	1	2.2	-1.2	1
9581	1961-08-21	ARCTIC BAY	NU	2400404	-84.62	72.98	10	-0.4	0.6	-1	1
9582	1961-08-22	ARCTIC BAY	NU	2400404	-84.62	72.98	10	-2.3	-1.1	-1.2	1
9583	1961-08-23	ARCTIC BAY	NU	2400404	-84.62	72.98	10	-1.1	0.6	-1.7	1
9584	1961-08-24	ARCTIC BAY	NU	2400404	-84.62	72.98	10	-0.3	0	-0.3	1
9585	1961-08-25	ARCTIC BAY	NU	2400404	-84.62	72.98	10	-1.1	0	-1.1	1
9586	1961-08-26	ARCTIC BAY	NU	2400404	-84.62	72.98	10	-2.8	-1.1	-1.7	1
9587	1961-08-27	ARCTIC BAY	NU	2400404	-84.62	72.98	10	-3.9	-2.2	-1.7	1

9588	1961-08-28	ARCTIC BAY	NU	2400404	-84.62	72.98	10	-4.9	-1.7	-3.2	1
9589	1961-08-29	ARCTIC BAY	NU	2400404	-84.62	72.98	10	-4.4	-1.1	-3.3	1
9590	1961-08-30	ARCTIC BAY	NU	2400404	-84.62	72.98	10	-1.6	-1.1	-0.5	1
9591	1961-08-31	ARCTIC BAY	NU	2400404	-84.62	72.98	10	-2.3	1.1	-3.4	1
9592	1961-09-01	ARCTIC BAY	NU	2400404	-84.62	72.98	10	-4.9	-1.7	-3.2	1
9593	1961-09-05	ARCTIC BAY	NU	2400404	-84.62	72.98	10	-2.3	-1.1	-1.2	1
9594	1961-09-06	ARCTIC BAY	NU	2400404	-84.62	72.98	10	-5.4	-3.3	-2.1	1
9595	1961-09-07	ARCTIC BAY	NU	2400404	-84.62	72.98	10	-6.7	-5.6	-1.1	1
9596	1961-09-09	ARCTIC BAY	NU	2400404	-84.62	72.98	10	-4.4	-1.1	-3.3	1
9597	1961-09-10	ARCTIC BAY	NU	2400404	-84.62	72.98	10	-5.8	-5.6	-0.2	1
9598	1961-09-12	ARCTIC BAY	NU	2400404	-84.62	72.98	10	-5.8	-5	-0.8	1
9599	1961-09-13	ARCTIC BAY	NU	2400404	-84.62	72.98	10	-5.3	-2.8	-2.5	1
9600	1961-09-15	ARCTIC BAY	NU	2400404	-84.62	72.98	10	-6.1	-5	-1.1	1
9601	1961-09-16	ARCTIC BAY	NU	2400404	-84.62	72.98	10	-6.1	-5	-1.1	1
9602	1961-09-17	ARCTIC BAY	NU	2400404	-84.62	72.98	10	-6.7	-5	-1.7	1
9603	1961-09-19	ARCTIC BAY	NU	2400404	-84.62	72.98	10	-9.2	-8.3	-0.9	1
9604	1961-09-24	ARCTIC BAY	NU	2400404	-84.62	72.98	10	-7.5	-6.1	-1.4	1
9605	1961-09-25	ARCTIC BAY	NU	2400404	-84.62	72.98	10	-7.9	-7.2	-0.7	1
9606	1961-09-28	ARCTIC BAY	NU	2400404	-84.62	72.98	10	-11.7	-11.1	-0.6	1
9607	1961-10-02	ARCTIC BAY	NU	2400404	-84.62	72.98	10	-8.4	-8.3	-0.1	1
9608	1961-10-04	ARCTIC BAY	NU	2400404	-84.62	72.98	10	-7.5	-5.6	-1.9	1
9609	1961-11-19	ARCTIC BAY	NU	2400404	-84.62	72.98	10	-17.9	-17.8	-0.1	1
9610	1962-06-11	ARCTIC BAY	NU	2400404	-84.62	72.98	10	1	1.1	-0.1	1
9611	1962-08-13	ARCTIC BAY	NU	2400404	-84.62	72.98	10	4	5	-1	1
9612	1962-08-18	ARCTIC BAY	NU	2400404	-84.62	72.98	10	-1.1	0	-1.1	1
9613	1962-08-27	ARCTIC BAY	NU	2400404	-84.62	72.98	10	-3.9	-2.2	-1.7	1
9614	1962-08-29	ARCTIC BAY	NU	2400404	-84.62	72.98	10	4	4.4	-0.4	1
9615	1962-08-31	ARCTIC BAY	NU	2400404	-84.62	72.98	10	2.4	2.8	-0.4	1
9616	1962-09-02	ARCTIC BAY	NU	2400404	-84.62	72.98	10	4	5	-1	1
9617	1962-09-05	ARCTIC BAY	NU	2400404	-84.62	72.98	10	-0.4	1.7	-2.1	1
9618	1962-09-06	ARCTIC BAY	NU	2400404	-84.62	72.98	10	1	2.2	-1.2	1
9619	1962-09-07	ARCTIC BAY	NU	2400404	-84.62	72.98	10	1	1.7	-0.7	1
9620	1962-09-09	ARCTIC BAY	NU	2400404	-84.62	72.98	10	-2.3	-0.6	-1.7	1
9621	1962-09-11	ARCTIC BAY	NU	2400404	-84.62	72.98	10	-3.4	-2.2	-1.2	1

9622	1962-09-12	ARCTIC BAY	NU	2400404	-84.62	72.98	10	-2.8	-2.2	-0.6	1
9623	1962-09-13	ARCTIC BAY	NU	2400404	-84.62	72.98	10	-3.4	-3.3	-0.1	1
9624	1962-09-14	ARCTIC BAY	NU	2400404	-84.62	72.98	10	-3.9	-2.8	-1.1	1
9625	1962-09-15	ARCTIC BAY	NU	2400404	-84.62	72.98	10	-4.4	-3.9	-0.5	1
9626	1962-09-17	ARCTIC BAY	NU	2400404	-84.62	72.98	10	-7.9	-6.7	-1.2	1
9627	1962-09-18	ARCTIC BAY	NU	2400404	-84.62	72.98	10	-5.8	-5.6	-0.2	1
9628	1962-09-27	ARCTIC BAY	NU	2400404	-84.62	72.98	10	-5.8	-5.6	-0.2	1
9629	1962-09-29	ARCTIC BAY	NU	2400404	-84.62	72.98	10	-2.8	-1.1	-1.7	1
9630	1962-10-05	ARCTIC BAY	NU	2400404	-84.62	72.98	10	-9.7	-9.4	-0.3	1
9631	1962-10-21	ARCTIC BAY	NU	2400404	-84.62	72.98	10	-8.4	-7.8	-0.6	1
9632	1962-10-23	ARCTIC BAY	NU	2400404	-84.62	72.98	10	-9.3	-8.9	-0.4	1
9633	1963-06-10	ARCTIC BAY	NU	2400404	-84.62	72.98	10	-2.8	-2.2	-0.6	1
9634	1963-06-27	ARCTIC BAY	NU	2400404	-84.62	72.98	10	0.9	1.7	-0.8	1
9635	1963-08-25	ARCTIC BAY	NU	2400404	-84.62	72.98	10	0.9	2.8	-1.9	1
9636	1963-08-29	ARCTIC BAY	NU	2400404	-84.62	72.98	10	-3.8	-1.7	-2.1	1
9637	1963-09-03	ARCTIC BAY	NU	2400404	-84.62	72.98	10	-1	0	-1	1
9638	1963-09-04	ARCTIC BAY	NU	2400404	-84.62	72.98	10	-1	-0.6	-0.4	1
9639	1963-10-04	ARCTIC BAY	NU	2400404	-84.62	72.98	10	-5.8	-5	-0.8	1
9640	1963-10-05	ARCTIC BAY	NU	2400404	-84.62	72.98	10	-5.7	-5	-0.7	1
9641	1963-11-07	ARCTIC BAY	NU	2400404	-84.62	72.98	10	-7.6	-6.7	-0.9	1
9642	1963-11-10	ARCTIC BAY	NU	2400404	-84.62	72.98	10	-5.8	-5	-0.8	1
9643	1963-11-11	ARCTIC BAY	NU	2400404	-84.62	72.98	10	-6.1	-5	-1.1	1
9644	1964-06-04	ARCTIC BAY	NU	2400404	-84.62	72.98	10	0.2	0.6	-0.4	1
9645	1964-06-09	ARCTIC BAY	NU	2400404	-84.62	72.98	10	-1.7	0.6	-2.3	1
9646	1964-06-10	ARCTIC BAY	NU	2400404	-84.62	72.98	10	-0.4	0.6	-1	1
9647	1964-06-14	ARCTIC BAY	NU	2400404	-84.62	72.98	10	-1.6	0.6	-2.2	1
9648	1964-06-20	ARCTIC BAY	NU	2400404	-84.62	72.98	10	-0.4	1.1	-1.5	1
9649	1964-06-24	ARCTIC BAY	NU	2400404	-84.62	72.98	10	-1.7	0	-1.7	1
9650	1964-06-27	ARCTIC BAY	NU	2400404	-84.62	72.98	10	1.8	2.2	-0.4	1
9651	1964-06-29	ARCTIC BAY	NU	2400404	-84.62	72.98	10	0.2	0.6	-0.4	1
9652	1964-06-30	ARCTIC BAY	NU	2400404	-84.62	72.98	10	0.2	0.6	-0.4	1
9653	1964-07-01	ARCTIC BAY	NU	2400404	-84.62	72.98	10	-0.4	0.6	-1	1
9654	1964-07-03	ARCTIC BAY	NU	2400404	-84.62	72.98	10	0.2	1.1	-0.9	1
9655	1964-09-04	ARCTIC BAY	NU	2400404	-84.62	72.98	10	0.2	1.7	-1.5	1

9656	1964-09-05	ARCTIC BAY	NU	2400404	-84.62	72.98	10	-0.4	0	-0.4	1
9657	1964-09-06	ARCTIC BAY	NU	2400404	-84.62	72.98	10	-1.6	0	-1.6	1
9658	1964-09-07	ARCTIC BAY	NU	2400404	-84.62	72.98	10	-2.8	-1.1	-1.7	1
9659	1964-09-08	ARCTIC BAY	NU	2400404	-84.62	72.98	10	-3.4	-2.8	-0.6	1
9660	1964-09-21	ARCTIC BAY	NU	2400404	-84.62	72.98	10	-0.4	1.1	-1.5	1
9661	1964-09-22	ARCTIC BAY	NU	2400404	-84.62	72.98	10	-2.8	-0.6	-2.2	1
9662	1964-09-23	ARCTIC BAY	NU	2400404	-84.62	72.98	10	-1.6	-1.1	-0.5	1
9663	1964-09-24	ARCTIC BAY	NU	2400404	-84.62	72.98	10	-2.3	-2.2	-0.1	1
9664	1964-10-13	ARCTIC BAY	NU	2400404	-84.62	72.98	10	-12.2	-11.1	-1.1	1
9665	1965-06-15	ARCTIC BAY	NU	2400404	-84.62	72.98	10	0.3	0.6	-0.3	1
9666	1965-07-18	ARCTIC BAY	NU	2400404	-84.62	72.98	10	0.3	0.6	-0.3	1
9667	1965-07-28	ARCTIC BAY	NU	2400404	-84.62	72.98	10	0.3	1.7	-1.4	1
9668	1965-08-29	ARCTIC BAY	NU	2400404	-84.62	72.98	10	-2.8	-1.7	-1.1	1
9669	1965-08-30	ARCTIC BAY	NU	2400404	-84.62	72.98	10	-3.4	-2.2	-1.2	1
9670	1965-09-03	ARCTIC BAY	NU	2400404	-84.62	72.98	10	-1.6	-1.1	-0.5	1
9671	1965-09-04	ARCTIC BAY	NU	2400404	-84.62	72.98	10	-2.3	-1.1	-1.2	1
9672	1965-09-09	ARCTIC BAY	NU	2400404	-84.62	72.98	10	-1.1	-0.6	-0.5	1
9673	1965-09-11	ARCTIC BAY	NU	2400404	-84.62	72.98	10	-2.8	-1.1	-1.7	1
9674	1965-09-12	ARCTIC BAY	NU	2400404	-84.62	72.98	10	-2.3	-1.1	-1.2	1
9675	1965-09-13	ARCTIC BAY	NU	2400404	-84.62	72.98	10	-3.9	-3.3	-0.6	1
9676	1965-09-14	ARCTIC BAY	NU	2400404	-84.62	72.98	10	-3.9	-2.2	-1.7	1
9677	1965-09-17	ARCTIC BAY	NU	2400404	-84.62	72.98	10	-2.8	-1.7	-1.1	1
9678	1965-09-20	ARCTIC BAY	NU	2400404	-84.62	72.98	10	-7.6	-7.2	-0.4	1
9679	1965-09-21	ARCTIC BAY	NU	2400404	-84.62	72.98	10	-9.3	-7.8	-1.5	1
9680	1965-09-26	ARCTIC BAY	NU	2400404	-84.62	72.98	10	-9.3	-8.9	-0.4	1
9681	1965-10-12	ARCTIC BAY	NU	2400404	-84.62	72.98	10	-7	-6.7	-0.3	1
9682	1966-03-29	ARCTIC BAY	NU	2400404	-84.62	72.98	10	-17.3	-17.2	-0.1	1
9683	1966-05-11	ARCTIC BAY	NU	2400404	-84.62	72.98	10	-7.8	-6.7	-1.1	1
9684	1966-05-21	ARCTIC BAY	NU	2400404	-84.62	72.98	10	-4.9	-3.9	-1	1
9685	1966-05-23	ARCTIC BAY	NU	2400404	-84.62	72.98	10	-7.5	-7.2	-0.3	1
9686	1966-05-26	ARCTIC BAY	NU	2400404	-84.62	72.98	10	-2.3	-1.7	-0.6	1
9687	1966-05-27	ARCTIC BAY	NU	2400404	-84.62	72.98	10	-3.4	-2.8	-0.6	1
9688	1966-05-30	ARCTIC BAY	NU	2400404	-84.62	72.98	10	-2.3	-1.1	-1.2	1
9689	1966-05-31	ARCTIC BAY	NU	2400404	-84.62	72.98	10	-3.4	-1.7	-1.7	1

9690	1971-05-06	ARCTIC BAY	NU	2400404	-84.62	72.98	10	-5.8	-4.4	-1.4	1
9691	1971-05-11	ARCTIC BAY	NU	2400404	-84.62	72.98	10	-8.9	-7.2	-1.7	1
9692	1971-05-22	ARCTIC BAY	NU	2400404	-84.62	72.98	10	-8.4	-7.2	-1.2	1
9693	1971-05-23	ARCTIC BAY	NU	2400404	-84.62	72.98	10	-7	-6.7	-0.3	1
9694	1971-05-24	ARCTIC BAY	NU	2400404	-84.62	72.98	10	-5.7	-4.4	-1.3	1
9695	1971-05-30	ARCTIC BAY	NU	2400404	-84.62	72.98	10	-8.9	-8.3	-0.6	1
9696	1971-06-10	ARCTIC BAY	NU	2400404	-84.62	72.98	10	-1.6	-1.1	-0.5	1
9697	1971-08-10	ARCTIC BAY	NU	2400404	-84.62	72.98	10	-0.4	0	-0.4	1
9698	1971-08-13	ARCTIC BAY	NU	2400404	-84.62	72.98	10	-1.6	-0.6	-1	1
9699	1971-08-24	ARCTIC BAY	NU	2400404	-84.62	72.98	10	3.2	3.3	-0.1	1
9700	1971-09-05	ARCTIC BAY	NU	2400404	-84.62	72.98	10	-2.8	-1.1	-1.7	1
9701	1971-09-06	ARCTIC BAY	NU	2400404	-84.62	72.98	10	-2.8	-2.2	-0.6	1
9702	1971-09-12	ARCTIC BAY	NU	2400404	-84.62	72.98	10	-2.3	-1.7	-0.6	1
9703	1971-09-17	ARCTIC BAY	NU	2400404	-84.62	72.98	10	-4.9	-3.3	-1.6	1
9704	1971-09-18	ARCTIC BAY	NU	2400404	-84.62	72.98	10	-4.4	-3.9	-0.5	1
9705	1971-09-24	ARCTIC BAY	NU	2400404	-84.62	72.98	10	-5.3	-4.4	-0.9	1
9706	1971-09-25	ARCTIC BAY	NU	2400404	-84.62	72.98	10	-5.3	-4.4	-0.9	1
9707	1971-09-27	ARCTIC BAY	NU	2400404	-84.62	72.98	10	-6.7	-6.1	-0.6	1
9708	1971-09-30	ARCTIC BAY	NU	2400404	-84.62	72.98	10	-4.4	-2.8	-1.6	1
9709	1971-10-03	ARCTIC BAY	NU	2400404	-84.62	72.98	10	-3.4	-2.8	-0.6	1
9710	1971-10-20	ARCTIC BAY	NU	2400404	-84.62	72.98	10	-6.2	-5.6	-0.6	1
9711	1974-10-01	ARCTIC BAY	NU	2400404	-84.62	72.98	10	-7	-4.4	-2.6	1
9712	1974-10-02	ARCTIC BAY	NU	2400404	-84.62	72.98	10	-6.2	-5.6	-0.6	1
9713	1974-10-05	ARCTIC BAY	NU	2400404	-84.62	72.98	10	-3.4	0	-3.4	1
9714	1974-10-06	ARCTIC BAY	NU	2400404	-84.62	72.98	10	-3.9	-1.7	-2.2	1
9715	1974-10-07	ARCTIC BAY	NU	2400404	-84.62	72.98	10	-5.3	-3.9	-1.4	1
9716	1974-10-09	ARCTIC BAY	NU	2400404	-84.62	72.98	10	-5.3	-4.4	-0.9	1
9717	1974-10-10	ARCTIC BAY	NU	2400404	-84.62	72.98	10	-4.9	-2.8	-2.1	1
9718	1974-10-11	ARCTIC BAY	NU	2400404	-84.62	72.98	10	-4.9	-4.4	-0.5	1
9719	1974-10-12	ARCTIC BAY	NU	2400404	-84.62	72.98	10	-7	-6.7	-0.3	1
9720	1975-05-19	ARCTIC BAY	NU	2400404	-84.62	72.98	10	-7.1	-6.7	-0.4	1
9721	1975-05-25	ARCTIC BAY	NU	2400404	-84.62	72.98	10	-3.4	-3.3	-0.1	1
9722	1975-06-01	ARCTIC BAY	NU	2400404	-84.62	72.98	10	0.2	0.6	-0.4	1
9723	1975-06-04	ARCTIC BAY	NU	2400404	-84.62	72.98	10	1.7	2.2	-0.5	1

9724	1975-06-23	ARCTIC BAY	NU	2400404	-84.62	72.98	10	-1.1	-0.6	-0.5	1
9725	1975-07-22	ARCTIC BAY	NU	2400404	-84.62	72.98	10	2.4	3.3	-0.9	1
9726	1975-07-23	ARCTIC BAY	NU	2400404	-84.62	72.98	10	3.1	3.3	-0.2	1
9727	1975-08-20	ARCTIC BAY	NU	2400404	-84.62	72.98	10	0.2	1.7	-1.5	1
9728	1975-08-21	ARCTIC BAY	NU	2400404	-84.62	72.98	10	-1.1	0	-1.1	1
9729	1975-08-23	ARCTIC BAY	NU	2400404	-84.62	72.98	10	-2.3	-0.6	-1.7	1
9730	1975-08-26	ARCTIC BAY	NU	2400404	-84.62	72.98	10	-2.8	-0.6	-2.2	1
9731	1975-08-28	ARCTIC BAY	NU	2400404	-84.62	72.98	10	1.8	2.2	-0.4	1
9732	1975-08-29	ARCTIC BAY	NU	2400404	-84.62	72.98	10	0.9	2.2	-1.3	1
9733	1975-08-30	ARCTIC BAY	NU	2400404	-84.62	72.98	10	-0.4	1.7	-2.1	1
9734	1975-08-31	ARCTIC BAY	NU	2400404	-84.62	72.98	10	0.9	1.1	-0.2	1
9735	1975-09-02	ARCTIC BAY	NU	2400404	-84.62	72.98	10	-4.4	-2.8	-1.6	1
9736	1975-09-03	ARCTIC BAY	NU	2400404	-84.62	72.98	10	-5.4	-2.8	-2.6	1
9737	1975-09-04	ARCTIC BAY	NU	2400404	-84.62	72.98	10	-5.4	-3.3	-2.1	1
9738	1975-09-05	ARCTIC BAY	NU	2400404	-84.62	72.98	10	-3.4	-2.8	-0.6	1
9739	1975-09-08	ARCTIC BAY	NU	2400404	-84.62	72.98	10	-5.4	-3.9	-1.5	1
9740	1975-09-10	ARCTIC BAY	NU	2400404	-84.62	72.98	10	-2.8	-1.1	-1.7	1
9741	1975-09-11	ARCTIC BAY	NU	2400404	-84.62	72.98	10	-3.4	-1.1	-2.3	1
9742	1975-09-13	ARCTIC BAY	NU	2400404	-84.62	72.98	10	-5.7	-4.4	-1.3	1
9743	1975-09-16	ARCTIC BAY	NU	2400404	-84.62	72.98	10	-7	-6.7	-0.3	1
9744	1975-09-17	ARCTIC BAY	NU	2400404	-84.62	72.98	10	-8.4	-7.2	-1.2	1
9745	1975-09-21	ARCTIC BAY	NU	2400404	-84.62	72.98	10	-5.4	-3.3	-2.1	1
9746	1975-09-27	ARCTIC BAY	NU	2400404	-84.62	72.98	10	-8.4	-8.3	-0.1	1
9747	1975-10-16	ARCTIC BAY	NU	2400404	-84.62	72.98	10	-10.9	-10.6	-0.3	1
9748	1976-04-28	ARCTIC BAY	NU	2400404	-84.62	72.98	10	-7.5	-6.1	-1.4	1
9749	1976-04-29	ARCTIC BAY	NU	2400404	-84.62	72.98	10	-12.6	-12.2	-0.4	1
9750	1976-05-20	ARCTIC BAY	NU	2400404	-84.62	72.98	10	-8.3	-7.2	-1.1	1
9751	1976-06-02	ARCTIC BAY	NU	2400404	-84.62	72.98	10	-3.4	-3.3	-0.1	1
9752	1976-06-05	ARCTIC BAY	NU	2400404	-84.62	72.98	10	-4.4	-2.2	-2.2	1
9753	1976-06-12	ARCTIC BAY	NU	2400404	-84.62	72.98	10	-2.3	0.6	-2.9	1
9754	1976-06-17	ARCTIC BAY	NU	2400404	-84.62	72.98	10	-1.1	0.6	-1.7	1
9755	1976-06-18	ARCTIC BAY	NU	2400404	-84.62	72.98	10	-1.7	1.1	-2.8	1
9756	1976-06-30	ARCTIC BAY	NU	2400404	-84.62	72.98	10	-1.1	0	-1.1	1
9757	1976-07-02	ARCTIC BAY	NU	2400404	-84.62	72.98	10	0.9	1.7	-0.8	1

9758	1976-07-09	ARCTIC BAY	NU	2400404	-84.62	72.98	10	1.6	1.7	-0.1	1
9759	1976-07-10	ARCTIC BAY	NU	2400404	-84.62	72.98	10	0.3	1.1	-0.8	1
9760	1976-07-11	ARCTIC BAY	NU	2400404	-84.62	72.98	10	-0.4	0.6	-1	1
9761	1976-08-06	ARCTIC BAY	NU	2400404	-84.62	72.98	10	0.9	2.2	-1.3	1
9762	1976-08-07	ARCTIC BAY	NU	2400404	-84.62	72.98	10	0.3	1.7	-1.4	1
9763	1976-08-08	ARCTIC BAY	NU	2400404	-84.62	72.98	10	0.9	1.7	-0.8	1
9764	1976-08-10	ARCTIC BAY	NU	2400404	-84.62	72.98	10	2.5	2.8	-0.3	1
9765	1976-08-11	ARCTIC BAY	NU	2400404	-84.62	72.98	10	0.9	2.8	-1.9	1
9766	1976-08-14	ARCTIC BAY	NU	2400404	-84.62	72.98	10	0.9	1.1	-0.2	1
9767	1976-08-19	ARCTIC BAY	NU	2400404	-84.62	72.98	10	3.2	3.3	-0.1	1
9768	1976-08-20	ARCTIC BAY	NU	2400404	-84.62	72.98	10	1.7	2.2	-0.5	1
9769	1976-08-21	ARCTIC BAY	NU	2400404	-84.62	72.98	10	-1.1	0	-1.1	1
9770	1976-08-22	ARCTIC BAY	NU	2400404	-84.62	72.98	10	-1.7	-0.6	-1.1	1
9771	1976-08-23	ARCTIC BAY	NU	2400404	-84.62	72.98	10	-1.7	0	-1.7	1
9772	1976-08-24	ARCTIC BAY	NU	2400404	-84.62	72.98	10	-1.7	-1.1	-0.6	1
9773	1976-08-25	ARCTIC BAY	NU	2400404	-84.62	72.98	10	-2.3	0	-2.3	1
9774	1976-08-26	ARCTIC BAY	NU	2400404	-84.62	72.98	10	-2.3	-0.6	-1.7	1
9775	1976-08-29	ARCTIC BAY	NU	2400404	-84.62	72.98	10	-1	0	-1	1
9776	1976-08-31	ARCTIC BAY	NU	2400404	-84.62	72.98	10	0.9	1.1	-0.2	1
9777	1976-09-03	ARCTIC BAY	NU	2400404	-84.62	72.98	10	-2.8	-1.1	-1.7	1
9778	1976-09-04	ARCTIC BAY	NU	2400404	-84.62	72.98	10	-3.4	-1.7	-1.7	1
9779	1976-09-05	ARCTIC BAY	NU	2400404	-84.62	72.98	10	-2.3	-0.6	-1.7	1
9780	1976-09-06	ARCTIC BAY	NU	2400404	-84.62	72.98	10	-0.4	0	-0.4	1
9781	1976-09-08	ARCTIC BAY	NU	2400404	-84.62	72.98	10	0.3	0.6	-0.3	1
9782	1976-09-11	ARCTIC BAY	NU	2400404	-84.62	72.98	10	-0.4	0	-0.4	1
9783	1976-09-12	ARCTIC BAY	NU	2400404	-84.62	72.98	10	-1.6	0	-1.6	1
9784	1976-09-13	ARCTIC BAY	NU	2400404	-84.62	72.98	10	-2.8	-1.1	-1.7	1
9785	1976-09-14	ARCTIC BAY	NU	2400404	-84.62	72.98	10	-2.8	-2.2	-0.6	1
9786	1976-09-15	ARCTIC BAY	NU	2400404	-84.62	72.98	10	-4.9	-3.9	-1	1
9787	1976-09-16	ARCTIC BAY	NU	2400404	-84.62	72.98	10	-6.1	-4.4	-1.7	1
9788	1976-09-17	ARCTIC BAY	NU	2400404	-84.62	72.98	10	-5.8	-3.9	-1.9	1
9789	1976-09-18	ARCTIC BAY	NU	2400404	-84.62	72.98	10	-6.6	-5	-1.6	1
9790	1976-09-19	ARCTIC BAY	NU	2400404	-84.62	72.98	10	-7	-5.6	-1.4	1
9791	1976-09-24	ARCTIC BAY	NU	2400404	-84.62	72.98	10	-4.4	-2.8	-1.6	1

9792	1976-09-25	ARCTIC BAY	NU	2400404	-84.62	72.98	10	-2.8	-2.2	-0.6	1
9793	1976-09-27	ARCTIC BAY	NU	2400404	-84.62	72.98	10	-3.4	-2.8	-0.6	1
9794	1976-09-29	ARCTIC BAY	NU	2400404	-84.62	72.98	10	-5.8	-4.4	-1.4	1
9795	1976-09-30	ARCTIC BAY	NU	2400404	-84.62	72.98	10	-5.4	-4.4	-1	1
9796	1976-10-02	ARCTIC BAY	NU	2400404	-84.62	72.98	10	-6.6	-4.4	-2.2	1
9797	1981-05-01	ARCTIC BAY	NU	2400404	-84.62	72.98	10	-17	-15	-2	1
9798	1982-09-05	ARCTIC BAY	NU	2400404	-84.62	72.98	10	-5	-3	-2	1
9799	1982-11-07	ARCTIC BAY	NU	2400404	-84.62	72.98	10	-23	-20	-3	1
9800	1991-03-10	ARCTIC BAY	NU	2400404	-84.62	72.98	10	-26.5	-25.5	-1	1
9801	1991-03-15	ARCTIC BAY	NU	2400404	-84.62	72.98	10	-22	-20.5	-1.5	1
9802	2005-10-10	ARCTIC BAY	NU	2400404	-84.62	72.98	10	-12.5	-12	-0.5	1
9803	2005-12-04	ARCTIC BAY	NU	2400404	-84.62	72.98	10	-29.5	-29	-0.5	1
9804	2009-03-27	ARCTIC BAY	NU	2400404	-84.62	72.98	10	-37	-30.5	-6.5	1
9805	2015-09-14	ARCTIC BAY	NU	2400404	-84.62	72.98	10	2.6	3.6	-1	1
9806	2015-09-15	ARCTIC BAY	NU	2400404	-84.62	72.98	10	0.2	2	-1.8	1
9807	2015-09-20	ARCTIC BAY	NU	2400404	-84.62	72.98	10	1.2	1.5	-0.3	1
9808	2015-09-21	ARCTIC BAY	NU	2400404	-84.62	72.98	10	0.3	0.9	-0.6	1
9809	2016-04-18	ARCTIC BAY	NU	2400404	-84.62	72.98	10	-16.2	-10.8	-5.4	1
9810	2016-04-20	ARCTIC BAY	NU	2400404	-84.62	72.98	10	-14.6	-13.7	-0.9	1
9811	1993-01-27	URANIUM CITY	SASK	406QLD0	-108.48	59.57	318	-26.6	-24	-2.6	1
9812	1993-01-28	URANIUM CITY	SASK	406QLD0	-108.48	59.57	318	-23.6	-14.1	-9.5	1
9813	1993-01-29	URANIUM CITY	SASK	406QLD0	-108.48	59.57	318	-12.8	-11.4	-1.4	1
9814	1993-06-20	URANIUM CITY	SASK	406QLD0	-108.48	59.57	318	8	11	-3	1
9815	1989-11-19	LOON LAKE	SASK	4064620	-109.1	54.05	546	-1	0	-1	1
9816	1989-11-21	LOON LAKE	SASK	4064620	-109.1	54.05	546	-13	-11	-2	1
9817	1987-11-18	BROCHET	MAN	5060520	-101.68	57.88	346	-18.5	-14	-4.5	1
9818	1987-11-23	BROCHET	MAN	5060520	-101.68	57.88	346	-7	-5	-2	1
9819	1990-01-07	BROCHET	MAN	5060520	-101.68	57.88	346	-17.5	-4	-13.5	1
9820	1991-08-27	BROCHET	MAN	5060520	-101.68	57.88	346	7.5	8	-0.5	1
9821	1993-10-25	BROCHET	MAN	5060520	-101.68	57.88	346	-5.5	-1.5	-4	1
9822	1994-08-14	BROCHET	MAN	5060520	-101.68	57.88	346	13.5	14	-0.5	1
9823	1996-04-09	BROCHET	MAN	5060520	-101.68	57.88	346	-3	-1	-2	1
9824	1997-04-14	BROCHET	MAN	5060520	-101.68	57.88	346	-10	-7	-3	1
9825	2007-01-09	BROCHET	MAN	5060520	-101.68	57.88	346	-29	-26	-3	1

9826	2007-01-17	BROCHET	MAN	5060520	-101.68	57.88	346	-23	-18	-5	1
9827	2008-05-02	BROCHET	MAN	5060520	-101.68	57.88	346	-15	-10	-5	1
9828	2008-05-05	BROCHET	MAN	5060520	-101.68	57.88	346	-10	-8	-2	1
9829	2008-05-06	BROCHET	MAN	5060520	-101.68	57.88	346	-11	-5	-6	1
9830	2008-05-08	BROCHET	MAN	5060520	-101.68	57.88	346	-14	-10	-4	1
9831	2008-05-09	BROCHET	MAN	5060520	-101.68	57.88	346	-14	-10	-4	1
9832	2008-05-13	BROCHET	MAN	5060520	-101.68	57.88	346	-8	1	-9	1
9833	2008-05-15	BROCHET	MAN	5060520	-101.68	57.88	346	-5	-1	-4	1
9834	2008-05-16	BROCHET	MAN	5060520	-101.68	57.88	346	4	14	-10	1
9835	2009-09-29	BROCHET	MAN	5060520	-101.68	57.88	346	-1	2	-3	1
9836	1926-11-11	HIGH PRAIRIE	ALTA	3063165	-116.48	55.4	602	-1.5	-1.1	-0.4	1
9837	1926-12-21	HIGH PRAIRIE	ALTA	3063165	-116.48	55.4	602	-23.4	-22.2	-1.2	1
9838	1927-06-17	HIGH PRAIRIE	ALTA	3063165	-116.48	55.4	602	12.2	12.8	-0.6	1
9839	1928-03-03	HIGH PRAIRIE	ALTA	3063165	-116.48	55.4	602	-2.7	-1.7	-1	1
9840	1936-09-12	HIGH PRAIRIE	ALTA	3063165	-116.48	55.4	602	0.6	1.1	-0.5	1
9841	1936-09-13	HIGH PRAIRIE	ALTA	3063165	-116.48	55.4	602	-1.5	-1.1	-0.4	1
9842	1937-01-18	HIGH PRAIRIE	ALTA	3063165	-116.48	55.4	602	-22.8	-22.2	-0.6	1
9843	1937-11-06	HIGH PRAIRIE	ALTA	3063165	-116.48	55.4	602	-0.8	0	-0.8	1
9844	1937-12-06	HIGH PRAIRIE	ALTA	3063165	-116.48	55.4	602	-11.5	-11.1	-0.4	1
9845	1938-01-10	HIGH PRAIRIE	ALTA	3063165	-116.48	55.4	602	-2.7	-2.2	-0.5	1
9846	1938-03-01	HIGH PRAIRIE	ALTA	3063165	-116.48	55.4	602	-4.9	-3.9	-1	1
9847	1939-10-05	HIGH PRAIRIE	ALTA	3063165	-116.48	55.4	602	-4.9	-4.4	-0.5	1
9848	1939-10-23	HIGH PRAIRIE	ALTA	3063165	-116.48	55.4	602	-8.9	-8.3	-0.6	1
9849	1940-01-13	HIGH PRAIRIE	ALTA	3063165	-116.48	55.4	602	-17.5	-16.1	-1.4	1
9850	1940-10-03	HIGH PRAIRIE	ALTA	3063165	-116.48	55.4	602	6.5	6.7	-0.2	1
9851	1942-12-16	HIGH PRAIRIE	ALTA	3063165	-116.48	55.4	602	-20.5	-20	-0.5	1
9852	1943-01-14	HIGH PRAIRIE	ALTA	3063165	-116.48	55.4	602	-2.2	-1.7	-0.5	1
9853	1943-02-06	HIGH PRAIRIE	ALTA	3063165	-116.48	55.4	602	-22.8	-21.1	-1.7	1
9854	1944-11-10	HIGH PRAIRIE	ALTA	3063165	-116.48	55.4	602	-6.5	-6.1	-0.4	1
9855	1944-11-24	HIGH PRAIRIE	ALTA	3063165	-116.48	55.4	602	-7.4	-6.7	-0.7	1
9856	1944-11-25	HIGH PRAIRIE	ALTA	3063165	-116.48	55.4	602	-13.1	-12.8	-0.3	1
9857	1945-01-06	HIGH PRAIRIE	ALTA	3063165	-116.48	55.4	602	-23.9	-23.3	-0.6	1
9858	1945-02-14	HIGH PRAIRIE	ALTA	3063165	-116.48	55.4	602	-25	-24.4	-0.6	1
9859	1945-03-03	HIGH PRAIRIE	ALTA	3063165	-116.48	55.4	602	-25	-23.9	-1.1	1

9860	1945-11-04	HIGH PRAIRIE	ALTA	3063165	-116.48	55.4	602	-3.8	-2.8	-1	1
9861	1945-11-05	HIGH PRAIRIE	ALTA	3063165	-116.48	55.4	602	-16.3	-16.1	-0.2	1
9862	1946-09-21	HIGH PRAIRIE	ALTA	3063165	-116.48	55.4	602	0.5	1.7	-1.2	1
9863	1946-11-14	HIGH PRAIRIE	ALTA	3063165	-116.48	55.4	602	-5.9	-5	-0.9	1
9864	1946-12-26	HIGH PRAIRIE	ALTA	3063165	-116.48	55.4	602	-24.5	-24.4	-0.1	1
9865	1946-12-31	HIGH PRAIRIE	ALTA	3063165	-116.48	55.4	602	-22.8	-22.2	-0.6	1
9866	1947-05-09	HIGH PRAIRIE	ALTA	3063165	-116.48	55.4	602	7.5	8.3	-0.8	1
9867	1947-09-20	HIGH PRAIRIE	ALTA	3063165	-116.48	55.4	602	7	7.2	-0.2	1
9868	1947-11-13	HIGH PRAIRIE	ALTA	3063165	-116.48	55.4	602	-9.4	-8.9	-0.5	1
9869	1948-12-31	HIGH PRAIRIE	ALTA	3063165	-116.48	55.4	602	-9.9	-9.4	-0.5	1
9870	1949-01-21	HIGH PRAIRIE	ALTA	3063165	-116.48	55.4	602	-24.5	-24.4	-0.1	1
9871	1949-07-16	HIGH PRAIRIE	ALTA	3063165	-116.48	55.4	602	14.1	14.4	-0.3	1
9872	1949-11-10	HIGH PRAIRIE	ALTA	3063165	-116.48	55.4	602	-0.2	0	-0.2	1
9873	1949-12-16	HIGH PRAIRIE	ALTA	3063165	-116.48	55.4	602	-18.7	-17.8	-0.9	1
9874	1950-02-04	HIGH PRAIRIE	ALTA	3063165	-116.48	55.4	602	-25	-23.9	-1.1	1
9875	1950-11-27	HIGH PRAIRIE	ALTA	3063165	-116.48	55.4	602	-18.1	-17.8	-0.3	1
9876	1983-09-26	HIGH PRAIRIE	ALTA	3063165	-116.48	55.4	602	1.5	2.5	-1	1
9877	1984-01-12	HIGH PRAIRIE	ALTA	3063165	-116.48	55.4	602	-18	-17	-1	1
9878	1984-01-23	HIGH PRAIRIE	ALTA	3063165	-116.48	55.4	602	-11.5	-9.5	-2	1
9879	1986-01-19	HIGH PRAIRIE	ALTA	3063165	-116.48	55.4	602	-14	-10	-4	1
9880	1990-01-12	HIGH PRAIRIE	ALTA	3063165	-116.48	55.4	602	-4	-1	-3	1
9881	1990-12-18	KEG RIVER	ALTA	3073641	-117.62	57.75	405	-30.5	-30	-0.5	1
9882	1970-01-03	NAIN	NFLD	8502800	-61.68	56.55	6	-10.2	-9.8	-0.4	1
9883	1970-01-14	NAIN	NFLD	8502800	-61.68	56.55	6	-8.4	-5.6	-2.8	1
9884	1970-01-15	NAIN	NFLD	8502800	-61.68	56.55	6	-10.2	-8.6	-1.6	1
9885	1970-01-20	NAIN	NFLD	8502800	-61.68	56.55	6	-10.2	-6.7	-3.5	1
9886	1970-03-10	NAIN	NFLD	8502800	-61.68	56.55	6	1.5	2.4	-0.9	1
9887	1971-01-02	NAIN	NFLD	8502800	-61.68	56.55	6	-10	-8.5	-1.5	1
9888	1971-02-26	NAIN	NFLD	8502800	-61.68	56.55	6	-10.9	-9.7	-1.2	1
9889	1971-03-13	NAIN	NFLD	8502800	-61.68	56.55	6	-9.1	-8.4	-0.7	1
9890	1971-06-24	NAIN	NFLD	8502800	-61.68	56.55	6	2.1	3	-0.9	1
9891	1972-04-07	NAIN	NFLD	8502800	-61.68	56.55	6	-9.2	-9	-0.2	1
9892	1975-03-27	NAIN	NFLD	8502800	-61.68	56.55	6	-10	-9.4	-0.6	1
9893	1985-01-29	NAIN	NFLD	8502800	-61.68	56.55	6	-12.7	-10.5	-2.2	1

9894	1985-01-30	NAIN	NFLD	8502800	-61.68	56.55	6	-13.8	-13.4	-0.4	1
9895	1987-02-19	NAIN	NFLD	8502800	-61.68	56.55	6	-12.4	-11.6	-0.8	1
9896	2013-04-17	NAIN	NFLD	8502800	-61.68	56.55	6	-5.5	-4.7	-0.8	1
9897	1983-10-19	FORT MCPHERSON	NWT	2201601	-134.85	67.4	35	-20	-19	-1	1
9898	2006-10-15	FORT MCPHERSON	NWT	2201601	-134.85	67.4	35	-4.6	-1.4	-3.2	1
9899	2006-10-26	FORT MCPHERSON	NWT	2201601	-134.85	67.4	35	-7.8	-6.4	-1.4	1
9900	2006-10-30	FORT MCPHERSON	NWT	2201601	-134.85	67.4	35	-10.2	-10.1	-0.1	1
9901	1959-12-31	CAPE DYER	NU	2400650	-61.38	66.65	725	-23.7	-22.8	-0.9	1
9902	1960-12-19	CAPE DYER	NU	2400650	-61.38	66.65	725	-12.6	-11.6	-1	1
9903	1962-03-13	CAPE DYER	NU	2400650	-61.38	66.65	725	-8.9	-8.7	-0.2	1
9904	1962-03-26	CAPE DYER	NU	2400650	-61.38	66.65	725	-12.6	-12.2	-0.4	1
9905	1994-11-27	CAPE DYER	NU	2400650	-61.38	66.65	725	-21.9	-21.1	-0.8	1
9906	1995-05-24	CAPE DYER	NU	2400650	-61.38	66.65	725	-6.4	-4.3	-2.1	1
9907	1998-01-23	CAPE DYER	NU	2400650	-61.38	66.65	725	-23.1	-17.4	-5.7	1
9908	1998-01-24	CAPE DYER	NU	2400650	-61.38	66.65	725	-23.7	-15.7	-8	1
9909	1998-09-23	CAPE DYER	NU	2400650	-61.38	66.65	725	-3.3	-3.2	-0.1	1
9910	1999-04-25	CAPE DYER	NU	2400650	-61.38	66.65	725	-11.2	-9.7	-1.5	1
9911	1951-10-04	LA SARRE	QUE	7094120	-79.22	48.78	244	16.7	17	-0.3	1
9912	1951-11-26	LA SARRE	QUE	7094120	-79.22	48.78	244	-5	-4.6	-0.4	1
9913	1952-01-27	LA SARRE	QUE	7094120	-79.22	48.78	244	-16.7	-16.6	-0.1	1
9914	1952-03-05	LA SARRE	QUE	7094120	-79.22	48.78	244	-11.7	-11.1	-0.6	1
9915	1952-04-10	LA SARRE	QUE	7094120	-79.22	48.78	244	-7.8	-6.2	-1.6	1
9916	1952-07-08	LA SARRE	QUE	7094120	-79.22	48.78	244	21.1	21.4	-0.3	1
9917	1952-09-02	LA SARRE	QUE	7094120	-79.22	48.78	244	16.7	17	-0.3	1
9918	1953-01-02	LA SARRE	QUE	7094120	-79.22	48.78	244	-5.6	-4.7	-0.9	1
9919	1953-01-11	LA SARRE	QUE	7094120	-79.22	48.78	244	-10.6	-9.9	-0.7	1
9920	1953-02-27	LA SARRE	QUE	7094120	-79.22	48.78	244	-10.6	-9.8	-0.8	1
9921	1953-06-09	LA SARRE	QUE	7094120	-79.22	48.78	244	11.7	12.3	-0.6	1
9922	1953-12-12	LA SARRE	QUE	7094120	-79.22	48.78	244	-6.1	-5.2	-0.9	1
9923	1954-01-16	LA SARRE	QUE	7094120	-79.22	48.78	244	-22.2	-21.3	-0.9	1
9924	1954-03-26	LA SARRE	QUE	7094120	-79.22	48.78	244	-6.1	-5.6	-0.5	1
9925	1954-05-25	LA SARRE	QUE	7094120	-79.22	48.78	244	11.7	12.9	-1.2	1
9926	1954-11-30	LA SARRE	QUE	7094120	-79.22	48.78	244	-5	-4.8	-0.2	1
9927	1954-12-01	LA SARRE	QUE	7094120	-79.22	48.78	244	-8.9	-8.6	-0.3	1

9928	1954-12-12	LA SARRE	QUE	7094120	-79.22	48.78	244	-10.6	-9.2	-1.4	1
9929	1954-12-19	LA SARRE	QUE	7094120	-79.22	48.78	244	-13.9	-13.6	-0.3	1
9930	1955-12-25	LA SARRE	QUE	7094120	-79.22	48.78	244	-13.9	-13.8	-0.1	1
9931	1955-12-31	LA SARRE	QUE	7094120	-79.22	48.78	244	-16.7	-14.8	-1.9	1
9932	1956-09-30	LA SARRE	QUE	7094120	-79.22	48.78	244	3.3	4.1	-0.8	1
9933	1956-11-08	LA SARRE	QUE	7094120	-79.22	48.78	244	3.3	3.9	-0.6	1
9934	1956-12-04	LA SARRE	QUE	7094120	-79.22	48.78	244	-16.7	-16.4	-0.3	1
9935	1956-12-12	LA SARRE	QUE	7094120	-79.22	48.78	244	-18.3	-17	-1.3	1
9936	1956-12-16	LA SARRE	QUE	7094120	-79.22	48.78	244	-11.7	-11.6	-0.1	1
9937	1956-12-17	LA SARRE	QUE	7094120	-79.22	48.78	244	-15	-13.8	-1.2	1
9938	1956-12-28	LA SARRE	QUE	7094120	-79.22	48.78	244	-12.2	-11.9	-0.3	1
9939	1956-12-29	LA SARRE	QUE	7094120	-79.22	48.78	244	-17.8	-17	-0.8	1
9940	1957-10-23	LA SARRE	QUE	7094120	-79.22	48.78	244	0	0.6	-0.6	1
9941	1957-11-09	LA SARRE	QUE	7094120	-79.22	48.78	244	0.6	1.9	-1.3	1
9942	1957-11-17	LA SARRE	QUE	7094120	-79.22	48.78	244	0.6	1.9	-1.3	1
9943	1957-12-21	LA SARRE	QUE	7094120	-79.22	48.78	244	1.7	1.9	-0.2	1
9944	1957-12-29	LA SARRE	QUE	7094120	-79.22	48.78	244	-15	-14.3	-0.7	1
9945	1958-01-18	LA SARRE	QUE	7094120	-79.22	48.78	244	-20.6	-20.1	-0.5	1
9946	1958-11-19	LA SARRE	QUE	7094120	-79.22	48.78	244	1.1	1.5	-0.4	1
9947	1958-11-27	LA SARRE	QUE	7094120	-79.22	48.78	244	-11.1	-11	-0.1	1
9948	1958-12-16	LA SARRE	QUE	7094120	-79.22	48.78	244	-22.8	-21.5	-1.3	1
9949	1958-12-19	LA SARRE	QUE	7094120	-79.22	48.78	244	-22.8	-22.3	-0.5	1
9950	1959-01-03	LA SARRE	QUE	7094120	-79.22	48.78	244	-11.7	-11.5	-0.2	1
9951	1959-01-04	LA SARRE	QUE	7094120	-79.22	48.78	244	-22.2	-20.9	-1.3	1
9952	1959-01-16	LA SARRE	QUE	7094120	-79.22	48.78	244	-17.2	-17	-0.2	1
9953	1959-01-22	LA SARRE	QUE	7094120	-79.22	48.78	244	-17.8	-16.4	-1.4	1
9954	1959-03-04	LA SARRE	QUE	7094120	-79.22	48.78	244	-5.6	-5.3	-0.3	1
9955	1959-05-14	LA SARRE	QUE	7094120	-79.22	48.78	244	1.7	2.5	-0.8	1
9956	1959-12-05	LA SARRE	QUE	7094120	-79.22	48.78	244	-0.6	-0.4	-0.2	1
9957	1960-02-01	LA SARRE	QUE	7094120	-79.22	48.78	244	-14.4	-14.2	-0.2	1
9958	1960-02-07	LA SARRE	QUE	7094120	-79.22	48.78	244	-15.6	-14.8	-0.8	1
9959	1960-05-01	LA SARRE	QUE	7094120	-79.22	48.78	244	0	0.5	-0.5	1
9960	1960-11-27	LA SARRE	QUE	7094120	-79.22	48.78	244	3.3	4.4	-1.1	1
9961	1960-11-28	LA SARRE	QUE	7094120	-79.22	48.78	244	3.3	4.3	-1	1

9962	1960-12-07	LA SARRE	QUE	7094120	-79.22	48.78	244	-12.8	-12.5	-0.3	1
9963	1960-12-16	LA SARRE	QUE	7094120	-79.22	48.78	244	-13.9	-12.8	-1.1	1
9964	1961-01-15	LA SARRE	QUE	7094120	-79.22	48.78	244	-27.8	-25.4	-2.4	1
9965	1961-07-03	LA SARRE	QUE	7094120	-79.22	48.78	244	12.8	13	-0.2	1
9966	1961-10-26	LA SARRE	QUE	7094120	-79.22	48.78	244	2.2	2.6	-0.4	1
9967	1961-12-05	LA SARRE	QUE	7094120	-79.22	48.78	244	1.1	1.8	-0.7	1
9968	1962-01-12	LA SARRE	QUE	7094120	-79.22	48.78	244	-12.8	-12.5	-0.3	1
9969	1962-01-15	LA SARRE	QUE	7094120	-79.22	48.78	244	-12.8	-12.1	-0.7	1
9970	1905-05-11	BERENS RIVER	MAN	5030203	-97.03	52.35	222	10	10.5	-0.5	1
9971	1906-10-02	BERENS RIVER	MAN	5030203	-97.03	52.35	222	8.3	8.4	-0.1	1
9972	1906-10-25	BERENS RIVER	MAN	5030203	-97.03	52.35	222	3.9	6.2	-2.3	1
9973	1909-10-15	BERENS RIVER	MAN	5030203	-97.03	52.35	222	3.9	4.1	-0.2	1
9974	1909-10-16	BERENS RIVER	MAN	5030203	-97.03	52.35	222	4.4	5.4	-1	1
9975	1909-10-22	BERENS RIVER	MAN	5030203	-97.03	52.35	222	1.7	3.1	-1.4	1
9976	1909-10-25	BERENS RIVER	MAN	5030203	-97.03	52.35	222	6.1	7.8	-1.7	1
9977	1909-11-03	BERENS RIVER	MAN	5030203	-97.03	52.35	222	4.4	5	-0.6	1
9978	1909-11-26	BERENS RIVER	MAN	5030203	-97.03	52.35	222	-11.7	-11.5	-0.2	1
9979	1910-03-23	BERENS RIVER	MAN	5030203	-97.03	52.35	222	9.4	10.1	-0.7	1
9980	1910-05-09	BERENS RIVER	MAN	5030203	-97.03	52.35	222	5.6	7	-1.4	1
9981	1910-05-10	BERENS RIVER	MAN	5030203	-97.03	52.35	222	3.9	6.3	-2.4	1
9982	1910-05-11	BERENS RIVER	MAN	5030203	-97.03	52.35	222	1.7	4.3	-2.6	1
9983	1910-05-23	BERENS RIVER	MAN	5030203	-97.03	52.35	222	10	11.3	-1.3	1
9984	1910-05-24	BERENS RIVER	MAN	5030203	-97.03	52.35	222	5	9.6	-4.6	1
9985	1910-06-03	BERENS RIVER	MAN	5030203	-97.03	52.35	222	9.4	10.4	-1	1
9986	1910-06-04	BERENS RIVER	MAN	5030203	-97.03	52.35	222	10.6	10.9	-0.3	1
9987	1910-09-05	BERENS RIVER	MAN	5030203	-97.03	52.35	222	11.1	11.2	-0.1	1
9988	1910-09-25	BERENS RIVER	MAN	5030203	-97.03	52.35	222	7.2	7.8	-0.6	1
9989	1910-11-26	BERENS RIVER	MAN	5030203	-97.03	52.35	222	-6.7	-5.9	-0.8	1
9990	1910-12-10	BERENS RIVER	MAN	5030203	-97.03	52.35	222	-12.2	-11.6	-0.6	1
9991	1911-05-27	BERENS RIVER	MAN	5030203	-97.03	52.35	222	4.4	6.1	-1.7	1
9992	1911-10-01	BERENS RIVER	MAN	5030203	-97.03	52.35	222	9.4	9.6	-0.2	1
9993	1911-10-02	BERENS RIVER	MAN	5030203	-97.03	52.35	222	4.4	9	-4.6	1
9994	1911-10-03	BERENS RIVER	MAN	5030203	-97.03	52.35	222	8.3	10.6	-2.3	1
9995	1911-10-17	BERENS RIVER	MAN	5030203	-97.03	52.35	222	10	10.3	-0.3	1

9996	1911-11-14	BERENS RIVER	MAN	5030203	-97.03	52.35	222	-19.4	-18.9	-0.5	1
9997	1911-12-11	BERENS RIVER	MAN	5030203	-97.03	52.35	222	-11.1	-11	-0.1	1
9998	1912-01-29	BERENS RIVER	MAN	5030203	-97.03	52.35	222	-26.7	-25.8	-0.9	1
9999	1912-04-28	BERENS RIVER	MAN	5030203	-97.03	52.35	222	1.1	2.9	-1.8	1
10000	1912-05-03	BERENS RIVER	MAN	5030203	-97.03	52.35	222	5.6	9	-3.4	1
10001	1912-05-04	BERENS RIVER	MAN	5030203	-97.03	52.35	222	6.7	8.4	-1.7	1
10002	1912-10-23	BERENS RIVER	MAN	5030203	-97.03	52.35	222	4.4	5.4	-1	1
10003	1912-11-01	BERENS RIVER	MAN	5030203	-97.03	52.35	222	-2.8	-2.2	-0.6	1
10004	1913-03-28	BERENS RIVER	MAN	5030203	-97.03	52.35	222	-3.9	-3	-0.9	1
10005	1913-05-11	BERENS RIVER	MAN	5030203	-97.03	52.35	222	10.6	10.8	-0.2	1
10006	1913-10-12	BERENS RIVER	MAN	5030203	-97.03	52.35	222	6.1	7.1	-1	1
10007	1913-10-18	BERENS RIVER	MAN	5030203	-97.03	52.35	222	4.4	5.1	-0.7	1
10008	1913-10-23	BERENS RIVER	MAN	5030203	-97.03	52.35	222	2.2	3	-0.8	1
10009	1913-10-30	BERENS RIVER	MAN	5030203	-97.03	52.35	222	-5.6	-4.9	-0.7	1
10010	1913-11-14	BERENS RIVER	MAN	5030203	-97.03	52.35	222	-7.2	-7.1	-0.1	1
10011	1913-12-31	BERENS RIVER	MAN	5030203	-97.03	52.35	222	-20.6	-19.3	-1.3	1
10012	1914-04-16	BERENS RIVER	MAN	5030203	-97.03	52.35	222	5.6	6.3	-0.7	1
10013	1914-10-14	BERENS RIVER	MAN	5030203	-97.03	52.35	222	10	12	-2	1
10014	1915-01-07	BERENS RIVER	MAN	5030203	-97.03	52.35	222	-20.6	-20.4	-0.2	1
10015	1915-01-09	BERENS RIVER	MAN	5030203	-97.03	52.35	222	-20	-19.4	-0.6	1
10016	1915-04-04	BERENS RIVER	MAN	5030203	-97.03	52.35	222	5.6	7.1	-1.5	1
10017	1915-06-17	BERENS RIVER	MAN	5030203	-97.03	52.35	222	11.1	12.2	-1.1	1
10018	1916-10-04	BERENS RIVER	MAN	5030203	-97.03	52.35	222	7.2	9.6	-2.4	1
10019	1916-11-12	BERENS RIVER	MAN	5030203	-97.03	52.35	222	-10	-9.9	-0.1	1
10020	1917-02-07	BERENS RIVER	MAN	5030203	-97.03	52.35	222	-21.7	-20.9	-0.8	1
10021	1917-03-25	BERENS RIVER	MAN	5030203	-97.03	52.35	222	2.2	3.2	-1	1
10022	1917-09-28	BERENS RIVER	MAN	5030203	-97.03	52.35	222	10	11.3	-1.3	1
10023	1917-11-04	BERENS RIVER	MAN	5030203	-97.03	52.35	222	8.9	9.6	-0.7	1
10024	1918-01-02	BERENS RIVER	MAN	5030203	-97.03	52.35	222	-25	-24.6	-0.4	1
10025	1918-05-24	BERENS RIVER	MAN	5030203	-97.03	52.35	222	5.6	8.4	-2.8	1
10026	1918-11-03	BERENS RIVER	MAN	5030203	-97.03	52.35	222	2.2	2.5	-0.3	1
10027	1918-11-10	BERENS RIVER	MAN	5030203	-97.03	52.35	222	2.8	6.3	-3.5	1
10028	1918-11-11	BERENS RIVER	MAN	5030203	-97.03	52.35	222	0	1.1	-1.1	1
10029	1919-11-26	BERENS RIVER	MAN	5030203	-97.03	52.35	222	-20.6	-19.4	-1.2	1

10030	1920-01-14	BERENS RIVER	MAN	5030203	-97.03	52.35	222	-27.8	-27	-0.8	1
10031	1920-10-01	BERENS RIVER	MAN	5030203	-97.03	52.35	222	4.4	7.8	-3.4	1
10032	1920-10-18	BERENS RIVER	MAN	5030203	-97.03	52.35	222	7.8	9.6	-1.8	1
10033	1920-10-22	BERENS RIVER	MAN	5030203	-97.03	52.35	222	8.3	10.6	-2.3	1
10034	1920-10-24	BERENS RIVER	MAN	5030203	-97.03	52.35	222	7.2	10.1	-2.9	1
10035	1920-11-02	BERENS RIVER	MAN	5030203	-97.03	52.35	222	1.1	2.5	-1.4	1
10036	1920-11-03	BERENS RIVER	MAN	5030203	-97.03	52.35	222	2.8	6.2	-3.4	1
10037	1920-11-04	BERENS RIVER	MAN	5030203	-97.03	52.35	222	1.1	2.5	-1.4	1
10038	1920-11-05	BERENS RIVER	MAN	5030203	-97.03	52.35	222	0	1.5	-1.5	1
10039	1920-11-06	BERENS RIVER	MAN	5030203	-97.03	52.35	222	1.7	2.5	-0.8	1
10040	1920-12-14	BERENS RIVER	MAN	5030203	-97.03	52.35	222	-5.6	-5.4	-0.2	1
10041	1921-04-07	BERENS RIVER	MAN	5030203	-97.03	52.35	222	4.4	5.2	-0.8	1
10042	1921-04-22	BERENS RIVER	MAN	5030203	-97.03	52.35	222	1.7	2.7	-1	1
10043	1921-09-22	BERENS RIVER	MAN	5030203	-97.03	52.35	222	7.8	8.4	-0.6	1
10044	1921-09-23	BERENS RIVER	MAN	5030203	-97.03	52.35	222	8.3	9.1	-0.8	1
10045	1921-12-20	BERENS RIVER	MAN	5030203	-97.03	52.35	222	-28.9	-26.9	-2	1
10046	1922-03-01	BERENS RIVER	MAN	5030203	-97.03	52.35	222	-11.1	-11	-0.1	1
10047	1922-04-04	BERENS RIVER	MAN	5030203	-97.03	52.35	222	7.2	8.4	-1.2	1
10048	1922-04-05	BERENS RIVER	MAN	5030203	-97.03	52.35	222	5.6	8.4	-2.8	1
10049	1922-04-15	BERENS RIVER	MAN	5030203	-97.03	52.35	222	3.3	4.1	-0.8	1
10050	1922-09-12	BERENS RIVER	MAN	5030203	-97.03	52.35	222	11.1	11.3	-0.2	1
10051	1923-02-14	BERENS RIVER	MAN	5030203	-97.03	52.35	222	-28.9	-28.2	-0.7	1
10052	1923-11-14	BERENS RIVER	MAN	5030203	-97.03	52.35	222	2.2	2.9	-0.7	1
10053	1923-11-16	BERENS RIVER	MAN	5030203	-97.03	52.35	222	1.7	2.9	-1.2	1
10054	1923-11-19	BERENS RIVER	MAN	5030203	-97.03	52.35	222	1.1	2.8	-1.7	1
10055	1924-10-13	BERENS RIVER	MAN	5030203	-97.03	52.35	222	3.9	8.9	-5	1
10056	1924-11-03	BERENS RIVER	MAN	5030203	-97.03	52.35	222	-6.7	-5.4	-1.3	1
10057	1924-11-04	BERENS RIVER	MAN	5030203	-97.03	52.35	222	-7.8	-6.9	-0.9	1
10058	1924-11-12	BERENS RIVER	MAN	5030203	-97.03	52.35	222	-12.2	-10.8	-1.4	1
10059	1924-11-14	BERENS RIVER	MAN	5030203	-97.03	52.35	222	-13.3	-11.4	-1.9	1
10060	1924-11-17	BERENS RIVER	MAN	5030203	-97.03	52.35	222	-18.9	-18.8	-0.1	1
10061	1924-11-24	BERENS RIVER	MAN	5030203	-97.03	52.35	222	-12.2	-12	-0.2	1
10062	1924-11-25	BERENS RIVER	MAN	5030203	-97.03	52.35	222	-10.6	-9.6	-1	1
10063	1924-11-26	BERENS RIVER	MAN	5030203	-97.03	52.35	222	-11.1	-9	-2.1	1

10064	1924-11-28	BERENS RIVER	MAN	5030203	-97.03	52.35	222	-19.4	-18.8	-0.6	1
10065	1924-12-14	BERENS RIVER	MAN	5030203	-97.03	52.35	222	-26.1	-24.5	-1.6	1
10066	1924-12-15	BERENS RIVER	MAN	5030203	-97.03	52.35	222	-27.8	-27.5	-0.3	1
10067	1925-02-06	BERENS RIVER	MAN	5030203	-97.03	52.35	222	-11.1	-7.9	-3.2	1
10068	1925-04-19	BERENS RIVER	MAN	5030203	-97.03	52.35	222	5.6	6.2	-0.6	1
10069	1925-04-22	BERENS RIVER	MAN	5030203	-97.03	52.35	222	5.6	6.3	-0.7	1
10070	1925-04-23	BERENS RIVER	MAN	5030203	-97.03	52.35	222	4.4	5.2	-0.8	1
10071	1925-05-10	BERENS RIVER	MAN	5030203	-97.03	52.35	222	6.7	8.9	-2.2	1
10072	1925-05-24	BERENS RIVER	MAN	5030203	-97.03	52.35	222	7.2	7.9	-0.7	1
10073	1925-05-27	BERENS RIVER	MAN	5030203	-97.03	52.35	222	4.4	7.2	-2.8	1
10074	1925-05-28	BERENS RIVER	MAN	5030203	-97.03	52.35	222	5.6	6.3	-0.7	1
10075	1925-05-29	BERENS RIVER	MAN	5030203	-97.03	52.35	222	7.8	8.6	-0.8	1
10076	1925-12-10	BERENS RIVER	MAN	5030203	-97.03	52.35	222	-20.6	-18.8	-1.8	1
10077	1926-01-02	BERENS RIVER	MAN	5030203	-97.03	52.35	222	0.6	1.1	-0.5	1
10078	1926-10-14	BERENS RIVER	MAN	5030203	-97.03	52.35	222	8.3	8.6	-0.3	1
10079	1926-10-26	BERENS RIVER	MAN	5030203	-97.03	52.35	222	0.6	2.5	-1.9	1
10080	1926-10-27	BERENS RIVER	MAN	5030203	-97.03	52.35	222	3.3	5	-1.7	1
10081	1926-10-28	BERENS RIVER	MAN	5030203	-97.03	52.35	222	8.3	8.6	-0.3	1
10082	1926-12-02	BERENS RIVER	MAN	5030203	-97.03	52.35	222	-25.6	-22.1	-3.5	1
10083	1926-12-20	BERENS RIVER	MAN	5030203	-97.03	52.35	222	-9.4	-7.9	-1.5	1
10084	1927-04-08	BERENS RIVER	MAN	5030203	-97.03	52.35	222	0	0.2	-0.2	1
10085	1927-09-20	BERENS RIVER	MAN	5030203	-97.03	52.35	222	6.1	6.2	-0.1	1
10086	1927-09-27	BERENS RIVER	MAN	5030203	-97.03	52.35	222	4.4	6.2	-1.8	1
10087	1927-11-02	BERENS RIVER	MAN	5030203	-97.03	52.35	222	1.7	2.1	-0.4	1
10088	1927-11-05	BERENS RIVER	MAN	5030203	-97.03	52.35	222	-11.1	-8.4	-2.7	1
10089	1927-11-12	BERENS RIVER	MAN	5030203	-97.03	52.35	222	-11.1	-7.8	-3.3	1
10090	1927-11-17	BERENS RIVER	MAN	5030203	-97.03	52.35	222	-16.7	-16.4	-0.3	1
10091	1927-11-27	BERENS RIVER	MAN	5030203	-97.03	52.35	222	-15.6	-15.3	-0.3	1
10092	1927-11-28	BERENS RIVER	MAN	5030203	-97.03	52.35	222	-2.8	-2.5	-0.3	1
10093	1927-12-04	BERENS RIVER	MAN	5030203	-97.03	52.35	222	-25	-21.5	-3.5	1
10094	1927-12-06	BERENS RIVER	MAN	5030203	-97.03	52.35	222	-26.7	-26.3	-0.4	1
10095	1927-12-09	BERENS RIVER	MAN	5030203	-97.03	52.35	222	-32.2	-30.3	-1.9	1
10096	1927-12-11	BERENS RIVER	MAN	5030203	-97.03	52.35	222	-26.1	-25.1	-1	1
10097	1927-12-20	BERENS RIVER	MAN	5030203	-97.03	52.35	222	-15.6	-15.3	-0.3	1

10098	1928-01-05	BERENS RIVER	MAN	5030203	-97.03	52.35	222	-11.1	-8.9	-2.2	1
10099	1928-01-06	BERENS RIVER	MAN	5030203	-97.03	52.35	222	-8.9	-5.9	-3	1
10100	1928-01-07	BERENS RIVER	MAN	5030203	-97.03	52.35	222	-6.1	-5.4	-0.7	1
10101	1928-01-08	BERENS RIVER	MAN	5030203	-97.03	52.35	222	-10	-7.8	-2.2	1
10102	1928-01-09	BERENS RIVER	MAN	5030203	-97.03	52.35	222	-7.8	-5.9	-1.9	1
10103	1928-01-12	BERENS RIVER	MAN	5030203	-97.03	52.35	222	-4.4	-1.8	-2.6	1
10104	1928-01-20	BERENS RIVER	MAN	5030203	-97.03	52.35	222	-24.4	-23.9	-0.5	1
10105	1928-01-26	BERENS RIVER	MAN	5030203	-97.03	52.35	222	-27.8	-24.5	-3.3	1
10106	1928-01-27	BERENS RIVER	MAN	5030203	-97.03	52.35	222	-28.3	-26.9	-1.4	1
10107	1928-01-28	BERENS RIVER	MAN	5030203	-97.03	52.35	222	-23.3	-22.1	-1.2	1
10108	1928-02-07	BERENS RIVER	MAN	5030203	-97.03	52.35	222	-5.6	-3.2	-2.4	1
10109	1928-02-08	BERENS RIVER	MAN	5030203	-97.03	52.35	222	-7.2	-6.9	-0.3	1
10110	1928-02-12	BERENS RIVER	MAN	5030203	-97.03	52.35	222	-5.6	-3.9	-1.7	1
10111	1928-03-08	BERENS RIVER	MAN	5030203	-97.03	52.35	222	-22.2	-21.5	-0.7	1
10112	1928-04-04	BERENS RIVER	MAN	5030203	-97.03	52.35	222	-7.8	-5.9	-1.9	1
10113	1928-04-25	BERENS RIVER	MAN	5030203	-97.03	52.35	222	-4.4	-1.1	-3.3	1
10114	1928-05-21	BERENS RIVER	MAN	5030203	-97.03	52.35	222	8.3	9	-0.7	1
10115	1928-06-18	BERENS RIVER	MAN	5030203	-97.03	52.35	222	13.3	14	-0.7	1
10116	1928-11-19	BERENS RIVER	MAN	5030203	-97.03	52.35	222	-3.3	-1.1	-2.2	1
10117	1928-11-20	BERENS RIVER	MAN	5030203	-97.03	52.35	222	-1.1	0.2	-1.3	1
10118	1929-09-22	BERENS RIVER	MAN	5030203	-97.03	52.35	222	13.9	14.6	-0.7	1
10119	1929-11-01	BERENS RIVER	MAN	5030203	-97.03	52.35	222	1.1	1.3	-0.2	1
10120	1929-11-08	BERENS RIVER	MAN	5030203	-97.03	52.35	222	-1.1	0.2	-1.3	1
10121	1994-10-17	PARENT	QUE	7075800	-74.62	47.92	445	6.7	7.4	-0.7	1
10122	1994-10-25	PARENT	QUE	7075800	-74.62	47.92	445	4.5	4.9	-0.4	1
10123	1995-10-06	PARENT	QUE	7075800	-74.62	47.92	445	5.6	6.1	-0.5	1
10124	1997-01-08	PARENT	QUE	7075800	-74.62	47.92	445	-15.9	-13.4	-2.5	1
10125	1997-01-17	PARENT	QUE	7075800	-74.62	47.92	445	-30.5	-29.7	-0.8	1
10126	1997-01-18	PARENT	QUE	7075800	-74.62	47.92	445	-25.1	-20	-5.1	1
10127	1985-08-28	PORT AUXBASQUES	NFLD	8402975	-58.97	47.58	40	14.3	16.8	-2.5	1
10128	2000-08-15	PORT AUXBASQUES	NFLD	8402975	-58.97	47.58	40	18.1	18.4	-0.3	1
10129	1974-02-27	NORWAY HOUSE	MAN	5062040	-97.85	53.95	224	-12.8	-10	-2.8	1
10130	1986-05-26	OLD CROW	YT	2100805	-139.83	67.57	251	-3.5	-3	-0.5	1
10131	1989-11-18	OLD CROW	YT	2100805	-139.83	67.57	251	-22	-19.5	-2.5	1

10132	1989-11-23	OLD CROW	YT	2100805	-139.83	67.57	251	-25	-24	-1	1
10133	1999-01-17	OLD CROW	YT	2100805	-139.83	67.57	251	-31	-26.5	-4.5	1
10134	1999-01-24	OLD CROW	YT	2100805	-139.83	67.57	251	-34	-27.5	-6.5	1
10135	1999-01-25	OLD CROW	YT	2100805	-139.83	67.57	251	-41.7	-22	-19.7	1
10136	1989-08-26	POND INLET	NU	2403206	-77.97	72.7	62	0	3.6	-3.6	1
10137	1994-10-15	POND INLET	NU	2403206	-77.97	72.7	62	-9	-6.5	-2.5	1
10138	1995-03-11	POND INLET	NU	2403206	-77.97	72.7	62	-39	-37.9	-1.1	1
10139	1997-11-15	POND INLET	NU	2403206	-77.97	72.7	62	-33	-18.9	-14.1	1
10140	1997-11-17	POND INLET	NU	2403206	-77.97	72.7	62	-30	-13.2	-16.8	1
10141	1997-11-22	POND INLET	NU	2403206	-77.97	72.7	62	-32.5	-21	-11.5	1
10142	1996-05-13	ENNADAI LAKE	NU	2301102	-100.9	61.1	353	-7.5	-5.3	-2.2	1
10143	1996-06-22	ENNADAI LAKE	NU	2301102	-100.9	61.1	353	9.1	9.4	-0.3	1
10144	1996-10-11	ENNADAI LAKE	NU	2301102	-100.9	61.1	353	-8.8	-5.3	-3.5	1
10145	1996-10-12	ENNADAI LAKE	NU	2301102	-100.9	61.1	353	-4.1	-3.4	-0.7	1
10146	1996-10-19	ENNADAI LAKE	NU	2301102	-100.9	61.1	353	-5.8	-5.5	-0.3	1
10147	1996-10-25	ENNADAI LAKE	NU	2301102	-100.9	61.1	353	-9.3	-3.7	-5.6	1
10148	1996-11-22	ENNADAI LAKE	NU	2301102	-100.9	61.1	353	-15.7	-15.4	-0.3	1
10149	1997-01-10	ENNADAI LAKE	NU	2301102	-100.9	61.1	353	-33.4	-22	-11.4	1
10150	1997-01-16	ENNADAI LAKE	NU	2301102	-100.9	61.1	353	-28.4	-25.1	-3.3	1
10151	1997-01-27	ENNADAI LAKE	NU	2301102	-100.9	61.1	353	-35.2	-32.4	-2.8	1
10152	1979-01-26	LEBEL QUEVILLON	QUE	7094275	-76.97	49.05	305	-8	-4.4	-3.6	1
10153	1917-12-21	JENNER	ALTA	3023560	-111.2	50.72	755	-26.5	-15	-11.5	1
10154	1918-09-24	JENNER	ALTA	3023560	-111.2	50.72	755	5.4	6.1	-0.7	1
10155	1918-11-19	JENNER	ALTA	3023560	-111.2	50.72	755	-9	-6.7	-2.3	1
10156	1918-11-23	JENNER	ALTA	3023560	-111.2	50.72	755	-18.4	-15	-3.4	1
10157	1918-12-13	JENNER	ALTA	3023560	-111.2	50.72	755	-14.3	-12.8	-1.5	1
10158	1994-01-15	JENNER	ALTA	3023560	-111.2	50.72	755	-23	-21	-2	1
10159	2008-01-30	JENNER	ALTA	3023560	-111.2	50.72	755	-41.5	-33.5	-8	1